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**PHILOLOGY AND LANGUAGE EDUCATION:
MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES**

GULISTAN CITY, OCTOBER 23–24, 2025

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA’LIMI VAZIRLIGI**

**GULISTON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA**

**FILOLOGIYA VA TIL TA’LIMI:
ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR**
2025-YIL 23–24-OKTABR, GULISTON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО И ШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН**

**ГУЛИСТАНСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ
ИНСТИТУТ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ**

**ФИЛОЛОГИЯ И ЯЗЫКОВОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ:
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ**

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“O‘zbekiston Respublikasi **Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi** tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 5847-sonli Farmonida ko‘zda tutilgan vazifalardan biri – ilmiy izlanish yutuqlarini amaliyotga joriy etish yo‘li bilan fan sohalarini rivojlantirish, ya’ni xalqaro ilmiy hamjamiyatda e’tirof etilishiga xizmat qilishdir. Shu va boshqa tegishli farmonlarda va qarorlarda belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirish maqsadida **2025 yil 23–24 oktyabr** kunlari Guliston davlat pedagogika institutida

“FILOLOGIYA VA TIL TA'LIMI: ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR”

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya o‘tkazilgan. Konferensiya zamonaviy pedagogika va filologiyaning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzularini aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

Assalomu alaykum Xurmatli Mehmonlar, aziz ustozlar! Mamlakatimiz bugungi kunda jahon hamjamiyati ko‘z o‘ngida barcha sohalarda jadal rivojlanib bormoqda. Shu o‘rinda barcha tarmoqlar va sohalarda, eng avvalo, ta‘lim sohasi, sog‘liqni saqlash va qishloq xo‘jaligida keng islohotlar joriy etish bo‘yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 5 oktyabrdagi PF 6079-son “Raqamli O‘zbekiston – 2030” strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risidagi Farmoni, 2024-yil 2 fevral kuni PQ-54-son “Ta‘lim sohasidagi islohotlarni jadallashtirish bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 19.01.2022-yil 19-yanvardagi 34-son “Xorijiy tillarni o‘rganishni takomillashtirish bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori qabul qilindi. Mazkur farmon va qarorlar milliy ta‘lim sohasini yanada rivojlantirish, chet tillarni chuqur o‘rganish, bugungi O‘zbekiston imijining, uning dunyo arenasidagi nufuzining oshirishiga xizmat qilishi shubhasiz.

So‘nggi yillar davomida yoshlarni bugungi kun talabiga mos holda tarbiyalash, chet tillarni chuqur o‘rganish, bugungi yoshlarning kamida ikkita chet tilini mukammal bilishlariga qaratilgan tadbirlar davlat miqyosida amalga oshirilmoqda. Shuning uchun ham kun tartibiga ta‘lim transformatsiyasi sharoitida tillarni o‘qitish muammolari va istiqbollarini ta‘minlashdek dolzarb masala ko‘ndalang qo‘yilmoqda. Global axborot jamiyati shakllanayotgan davrda ta‘lim va tillarni o‘qitish masalalari milliy taraqqiyot, har bir fuqaroning mamlakat kelajagi uchun ijtimoiy faolligi va mas‘uliyati, mamlakatning dunyo miqyosidagi nufuzining oshirishini ta‘minlovchi muhim omildir.

Guliston davlat pedagogika institutida o‘tkazilayotgan “Filologiya va til ta‘limi: zamonaviy tendentsiyalar va innovatsion yondashuvlar” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasi soha mutaxassislarini ushbu masalani tadqiq etish, tillarni o‘qitish muammolari va istiqbollarini ta‘minlash, bu bo‘yicha olib borilayotgan yangi tadqiqotlar bilan tanishish, xorijiy tajribalarni o‘rganib, ularni amaliyotda qo‘llash, til o‘rganish madaniyatini shakllantirish bo‘yicha istiqboldagi islohotlarni chuqurlashtirish bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish, muammolarni zamonaviy yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilish imkoniyatini berishi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Mazkur anjuman mamlakatimiz tadqiqotchilarining sa‘y-harakatlari natijasi bo‘lib, ushbu anjuman materiallari ta‘lim, fan, shuningdek pedagogika sohasidagi mutaxassislar malakasini oshirishga yordam beradi, degan umiddamiz.

Konferentsiya to‘plami ta‘lim jarayonining asosiy subektlari bo‘lgan pedagog va talabalar ehtiyojini hisobga olgan holda tuzilgan bo‘lib, aynan ustoz-o‘qituvchilar millionlab yoshlarning iqtidorini, shu jumladan, ta‘lim va tarbiya madaniyatini shakllantiruvchi asosiy shaxslar bo‘lib hisoblanishi bilan dolzarbdir.

Guliston davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
J. X. Karshibaev

KONFERENSIYANING PLENAR VO'LIMI MA'RUZALARI
УНИВЕРСАЛЬНАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ТОПООБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ОБЩЕТЮРКСКОЙ
ТОПОНИМИИ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается процесс отражения этнической модели в топообразовании в общетюркской топонимической системе. Изучение проблемы позволило установить национально-этническое своеобразие и особую специфику формирования и функционирования общетюркской топонимической. В данном процессе образования топонимов казахского языка и узбекского языка установлена метафоричность имен. В статье также рассматривается влияние влиянием экстралингвистических факторов на общетюркскую топонимическую систему Центральноазиатского региона.

Ключевые слова: топоним, топонимическая система, гидроним, ойконим, этноним, этнотопоним, ирредент, национально-этническая модель.

Abstract: The article examines the process of reflecting the ethnic model in toponym formation within the common Turkic toponymic system. The study of this issue made it possible to identify the national and ethnic distinctiveness, as well as the specific features of the formation and functioning of the common Turkic toponymy. In this process, the metaphorical nature of place names in the Kazakh and Uzbek languages has been revealed. The article also analyzes the influence of extralinguistic factors on the common Turkic toponymic system of the Central Asian region.

Keywords: toponym, toponymic system, hydronym, oikonym, ethnonym, ethnonymic toponym, irredenta, national-ethnic model.

Все топонимические система мира обладают собственным своеобразием и особой спецификой формирования и функционирования. Обязательное качество – модель топообразовании. Общетюркская топонимическая система в иноязычном окружении также обладает неповторимой собственно этнической моделью *топообразования этнической модели топообразования казахского языка и узбекского языка* присуще исключительное богатство языковых приемов обозначения географических объектов.

В процессе образования топонимов *казахского языка и узбекского языка* мы довольно часто наблюдаем метафоричность, т.е. в составе имен объектов выступают названия частей тела животных или человека – анатомические термины. Например: тұмсық “клов” (Құстұмсық Сырд. р-н, РУз), кіндік “пупок” (Кіндік төбе Сырд. р-н, РУз), бас “голова” (Түлкібас ЮКО РК), емшек “груди” (Қыземшек ЮКО РК), мұрын “нос”, (Мұрынтау Навоийск. обл. РУз).

Часто при образовании географических названий наблюдается употребление цветowych прилагательных. Например: ақ “белый” (Ақсу ЮКО РК, Ақсу Бекабад. р-н, РУз), қара “черный” (Қаратау ЮКО РК, Қаратөбе Верхнечирчикск. р-н, РУз, Қарасу ЮКО РК, Қарасу Таш. обл. РУз), қызыл “красный” (Қызылсу ЮКО РК, Қызылбұлақ

Сырд. р-н, РУз), көк “зеленый” (Көксәйек ЮКО РК, Көкбұлақ Сырд. р-н, РУз, Көктерек Келесск. р-н, РУз), сары “желтый” (Сарыағаш ЮКО РК, Сарыарқа РК) и т.п.

Зачастую общетюркская топонимическая система в иноязычном окружении складывается и на территории обитания ирредентов в глубокой древности и сохраняет в себе этнические особенности создателей и носителей топонимической системы. Существование общетюркской топонимической системы с древности подтверждает наличие исконно казахских топообразующих языковых оронимических, гидронимических и других формантов, которые и являются концептуализирующими языковыми фактами. К примеру, концепт возвышенность выражен: тау “гора”(Қаржантау Бостандықск. р-н, РУз, Мұрынтау Навоийск. обл. РУз, Боқантау Навоийск. обл. РУз), төбе “холм” (Ақтөбе г. Ташкент, РУз, Тойтөбе Таш. обл. РУз, Бәйгетөбе Сырд. обл. РУз, Жаңғызтөбе Сырд. обл. РУз), қыр, адыр “гряда возвышенностей” (Қарақыр Мақтаралск. р-н, ЮКО РК, Дарбазақыр Хавастск. р-н, РУз), дөң “высокое место” (Боздөң Сырд. р-н, РУз, Дөңарық Мехнатабдск. р-н РУз), қия “косогор, небольшая возвышенность” (Қарақия, Қызылқия ЮКО РК), шоқы “вершина, пик, бугор, сопка” (Алтыншоқы РК, Мырзашоқы Мақтаралск р-н РК), шың “пик”(Хан Тәңірі шыңы РК), асу “перевал” (Қазығұрт асуы ЮКО РК).

Гидронимический концепт су «вода» также имеет широкий спектр выражения: дарья “река” (Сырдарья, Амударья, Қызылдарья, Өзгендарья). Су “речка” (Ақсу, Қарасу, Бозсу, Қызылсу); бұлақ “родник”; “ключ”, “источник” (Қарабұлақ ЮКО РК, Қотырбұлақ Таш. обл. РУз, Қотырбұлақ Джизакск. обл. РУз, Маржанбұлақ Джизакск обл. РУз); өзек “ручей” (Сорөзек Сырд. Обл. РУз, Майлыөзек Сырд. обл. РУз); сай “горный ручей” (Қызылсай Бостандықск. р-н РУз, Шұқырсай г. Ташкент, РУз, Майлысай, Киргизия, Арнасай РУз).

Ойконимический концепт елді мекен “населенный пункт”: кент “город” (Шымкент ЮКО РК, Құмкент ЮКО РК, Өзкент, Ташкент РУз); қала “город” (Аққала, Тасқала, Топыраққала Туркмения).

Перечисленные примеры позволяют нам определить характерные черты казахского топообразования в иноязычном окружении, однако надо отметить эти черты свойственны всей общеказахской топонимической системе.

Этнической модели топообразования общетюркской топонимической системы *казахского языка и узбекского языка* присуще:

- 1) отсутствие антропонимов в составе названий населенных пунктов;
- 2) обозначение аулов кишлаков этническим именем рода племени, аул здесь имеется в виду мобильное родовое сообщество, проживающее на строго определенной территории, перекочёвывающее, в зависимости от времени года и сезонного состояния пастбищ;
- 3) наличие в топонимических системах *казахского языка и узбекского языка* значительного количества этнотопонимов;
- 4) активное использование при обозначении географических объектов цветowych прилагательных;
- 5) значительность синонимического ряда при обозначении географических объектов;
- 6) языковая метафоричность при обозначении географических объектов;
- 7) использование в качестве метафоры анатомических терминов.

Однако во второй половине XIX века модель общетюркской топонимической системы подверглась сильной деформации. Это произошло в силу завоевания русским царизмом Центральноазиатских территорий. В топонимии данного региона появились

русские географические названия, отражающие имперскую идеологию и колониальную политику царского правительства. Следует отметить, что в дореволюционный период ойконимы антропонимического происхождения отражали идеологию и политику царского самодержавия в Туркестанском крае. Так, антропоойконимы этого времени были направлены:

а) на возвеличивание царской фамилии, например, Романовский, Николаевский, Никольский, Велико-Алексеевский и пр.;

б) захватническую политику правительства, т.е. отражали фамилию генералов царской армии. Например: посолок-станция Черняево, Хилково, железнодорожные разъезды Шамшинский, Сваричевский и др.

Таким образом, во второй половине XIX века в центральноазиатском регионе появляются русские географические названия, возникшие в связи с завоеванием Туркестана к Российской империи и началом колонизации всего этого обширного региона.

В топонимической системе любого региона воплощается историческое прошлое народов, обитающих на той территории. На любом этапе развития общества ономастическая система имела большое культурно-историческое значение. Национальная ономастическая система Казахстана, складывалась на протяжении многих столетий. На следующем этапе своего развития, начиная со второй половины XIX века, в результате захватнической политики Российской империи топонимия Казахстана была подвержена значительным изменениям. Еще более пагубное воздействие на топонимию, и в первую очередь на названия населенных пунктов (ойконимы) оказала политика советской власти. В результате пострадала самобытность, национальная специфика казахской ономастики, что в дальнейшем не могло не привести к размыванию национальной этноидентичности народа Центральной Азии.

В изучаемом регионе отмечались ойконимы, отражающие фамилии царских генералов: Фогелево (аул Рабат, ЮКО, Казыгуртский р-н), Ермоловка (аул Берген Исаханов, ЮКО, Ордабасынский район). Все без исключения общетюркские топонимы *казахского языка и узбекского языка большей частью* антропонимического происхождения. Значительная часть этих топонимов, связанные с низвергнутым большевиками царским режимом, были переименованы уже в советское время. Романовский переименован в Крестьянский (Узбекистан, Сырдарьинская область), Новоалексеевское (ныне г.Бахт, Узбекистан, Сырдарьинская область). Широко известная Черняевка, также названная в честь генерала Черняева, переименована в Полторацкое (ныне Жібек Жолы, Казахстан, ЮКО). Алексеевское уже трижды последовательно переименовывается: сначала в Ленинское, затем в Казыгурт и, наконец, Кыдыр Мамбетұлы (Казахстан, ЮКО) таких примеров больше, чем достаточно. Последние факты говорят о тех невероятных волнах переименований, которые прокатились по Центральной Азии за исторически короткий промежуток времени в сто пятьдесят лет.

В советский период возникает много антропоойконимов, связанных с именами революционных деятелей (Ф.Дзержинский, Я.Свердлов), военачальников гражданской войны (В.Чапаев, Д.Фурманов, К.Ворошилов, М.Фрунзе), организаторов советской власти (М.Калинин, В.Куйбышев, И.Жданов), строителей нового государства и представителей международного коммунистического движения (К.Маркс, Ф.Энтельс, Э.Тельман). Список этот далеко не полон и данный массив антропоойконимов может стать объектом самостоятельного исследования.

На первом месте в этом ряду находились названия объектов данные в честь основоположника советского государства В.И.Ленина. В качестве ойконимов использованы разные варианты его имени и отчества: Ленинабад (аул Сырабат, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н), Ленино (аул Аймантөбе, Жамбылская область, Байзакский р-н), Ленино (аул Ырысты, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н), Ленинское (аул Казыгурт ЮКО, центр Казыгуртского района), Ильич (посёлок Атакент, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н), Заветы Ленина (аул Қаныш Сәтбаев, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н), Путь Ильича (аул Мырзашоқы, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н). Практически в каждом регионе Южного Казахстана было большее или меньшее количество ойконимов, связанных с именем Ленина, более того в каждом ойкониме встречался годоним с этим именем.

Таким образом, в топонимической системе Центральной Азии необходимо констатировать продуктивность историко-мемориального принципа номинации объектов, возникших в течении XIX-XX веков, которые были связаны с конкретными историческими личностями и имели идеологическую коннотацию.

Определенная часть дореволюционных и послереволюционных ойконимов *казахского языка и узбекского языка* имеют миграционный характер: Славянка (посёлок Мырзакент, ЮКО, Мақтааралский р-н), Нововознесенка (аул Көктөбе, Жамбылская область, Жуалынский р-н), Новоивановка (аул Жетібай, Жамбылская область, Байзакский р-н), Новосёловка (аул Жаңатұрмыс, ЮКО, Сайрамский р-н), Новотроицкое (аул Төле Би, Жамбылская область, центр Шуйского района).

Этнические названия, как известно, особенно развиты у кочевых народов. Пастбища, луга, водные угодья, зимовки, летовки, принадлежавшие определенному роду и племени, четко ограничивались и назывались этническим именем владельцев. А.В.Суперанская замечает по этому поводу, что специфика добывания средств существования способствует тому, что кочевое племя досконально знает свою территорию, вплоть до мелких урочищ, и владеет топонимической системой, в которой представлены все природно-физические названия, но почти нет ойконимов (названий поселений).

В определенный исторический период в связи с коренными изменениями социально-экономических условий, казахи, проживающие испокон на территории современного Узбекистана, постепенно переходят на земледельческо-скотоводческий, а затем на земледельческий уклад хозяйствования. С полным переходом на земледелие, бывшие небольшие зимовья вырастают в населенные пункты, за которыми сохраняются этнические имена их обитателей, представителей казахских родов и племен. Именно поэтому, в Узбекистане наблюдаем большое количество казахских этноойконимов.

В новых исторических условиях был очень быстро разрушен традиционный кочевой образ жизни казахского народа, что в советское время было однозначно представлено как достижение: это называлось переходом от феодализма к социализму, минуя капиталистическую стадию развития. Названия населённых мест сразу стали важнее, чем названия природно-географических объектов, потому что туда переместились хозяйственные, политические и экономические центры жизни народа. В то же время ойконимы, которые всегда представляли большой идеологический интерес, подтвердили свою репутацию имён, подвергающихся наиболее частым изменениям. Это связано также с ростом городов, когда поглощаются близлежащие населённые пункты, и с вымиранием малых населённых пунктов, когда их названия исключаются из справочников различного назначения, исчезают с географических карт. А затем названия уходят и из народной памяти. Переименование названий,

продиктованное изменением политической, экономической, языковой и прочей ориентации, также является не менее важным фактором потери уникальной культурологической информации. Процессы эти исторически закономерны, остановить их невозможно, и на долю топонимики остаётся задача выявления и изучения происходящего в целях сохранения «уходящей природы» и разработка, по мере возможности и необходимости, научно обоснованных рекомендаций.

Таким образом, в процессе изучения этнической модели топообразования в общетюркской топонимической системе установлено: каждая топонимическая система мира обладает национально-этническим своеобразием и особой спецификой формирования и функционирования. Общетюркская топонимическая система в иноязычном окружении также обладает неповторимой собственноэтнической моделью топообразования. Этнической модели топообразования казахского языка и узбекского языка присуще исключительное богатство языковых приемов обозначения географических объектов. В данном процессе образования топонимов казахского языка и узбекского языка мы наблюдаем метафоричность, довольно часто при образовании географических названий наблюдается употребление цветowych прилагательных.

В силу экстралингвистических факторов, во второй половине XIX века модель общетюркской топонимической системы подверглась сильной деформации. Это произошло в силу завоевания русским царизмом Центральноазиатских территорий. В топонимии данного региона появились русские географические названия, отражающие имперскую идеологию и колониальную политику царского правительства. Интенсивный процесс идеологизации топонимических систем наблюдается и в советское время.

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ENHANCING CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article examines the developmental stages of creative competence in future English language teachers. The research identifies three essential phases-motivational-cognitive, activity-based, and reflective-analytical-each contributing to the teacher's creative and professional development. Emphasis is placed on the integration of digital tools, interactive tasks, and reflective practices. The article explores both local and international academic perspectives and offers practical examples in English language teaching. It also suggests new approaches such as the "Creativity Sandbox Model" to encourage innovation in pedagogical practices.

Keywords: creative competence, future English teacher, development stages, reflection, innovative education, motivation, communicative methods, digital tools.

In recent years, the development of creative competence among prospective English language teachers has become a key priority in Uzbekistan's education system. Presidential Decree No. PQ-5117 (May 19, 2019) emphasizes the need to introduce innovative teaching methods and prepare teachers who are capable of thinking creatively and using communicative strategies effectively.

Creative competence is now viewed as a core component of the modern teacher's professional identity. It goes beyond subject knowledge, encompassing the ability to design engaging lessons, apply innovative methodologies, and inspire creativity in students. For English teachers, this competence is crucial in transforming traditional classrooms into dynamic learning environments.

Creative competence refers to a teacher's ability to approach teaching innovatively, generate original ideas, solve problems flexibly, and foster creativity among students. According to Amabile (2018), intrinsic motivation is the driving force behind creativity. Similarly, Lubart (2021) and Robinson (2020) highlight creativity as an essential skill for 21st-century educators.

Following the frameworks proposed by Kolb (2019), Anderson (2021), and Begmatova (2023), the development of creative competence can be broken down into three interconnected stages:

1. Motivational-Cognitive Stage. At this stage, the future teacher develops internal motivation and a personal understanding of the value of creativity. This phase involves answering key questions such as:

Why is creativity necessary in teaching?

How can I inspire creative thinking in my students?

This phase relies heavily on intrinsic motivation. Amabile (2018) states, "Creativity does not stem from external rewards but from internal desire and self-expression." Accordingly, teachers must find personal meaning in innovating their lessons.

Classroom Techniques:

Story Completion Tasks: Encourage learners to invent and narrate endings.

"What if...?" Questions: Stimulate divergent thinking.

"Imagine the Situation" Scenarios: Spark imagination and linguistic creativity.

These strategies lay the groundwork for creative engagement by treating students as active contributors rather than passive listeners.

2. Activity-Based Stage. In this stage, future teachers apply creative methods in real teaching contexts. Based on Kolb's experiential learning theory, knowledge is best acquired through direct experience. Richards (2020) suggests that learners truly acquire language only when they are involved in its creation.

Effective Activities: Role Plays – Simulate real-life communication;

Creative Writing – Encourage linguistic experimentation;

Problem-Solving Tasks – Promote critical and creative thinking.

A task like “If I were a teacher, I would...” allows students to practice conditional grammar while proposing innovative teaching ideas. Such tasks simultaneously foster linguistic competence and pedagogical imagination.

Teachers should also adopt the role of facilitators-guiding rather than instructing, supporting learners in shaping their own creative expressions.

Digital Integration: Using platforms like Padlet, Canva, Jamboard, or Genially transforms the classroom into a virtual creativity lab. According to Anderson (2021), digital environments serve as incubators for creative thought and expression.

3. Reflective-Analytical Stage. The final stage focuses on evaluating and improving one's creative teaching practices. Reflection is not a conclusion but a continuous process of self-assessment and growth.

Golovko (2020) defines reflection as “the re-understanding of personal experience that leads to new pedagogical insights.”

Reflective Tools:

Learning Journals: Teachers document their teaching experiences;

Peer Feedback: Encourages collaborative evaluation;

Self-Assessment Forms: Promote metacognition and accountability.

For example, using prompts like “After my lesson today...” or “What I could improve next time...” in English encourages both language practice and self-analysis.

Creative Extension: The “Creativity Sandbox Model”. As an addition to the traditional three-stage model, this paper proposes the Creativity Sandbox Model—a flexible, safe environment where future teachers are encouraged to experiment with lesson ideas without the fear of failure. This "sandbox" could be implemented as a virtual platform or physical space within teacher training institutions.

This model aligns with Craft's (2019) idea that schools should nurture “possibility thinking” and reduce the constraints that limit innovation.

The development of creative competence in future English language teachers is a multi-layered, continuous process that must begin during teacher education. The three stages—motivational-cognitive, activity-based, and reflective-analytical—serve as a roadmap for fostering innovation in teaching practices.

Only by combining intrinsic motivation, experiential learning, reflective thinking, and digital innovation can we prepare teachers who are not only linguistically proficient but also creatively empowered. The inclusion of creative spaces, such as the Creativity Sandbox, further enhances the transformation of future educators into agents of change within the education system.

Ultimately, creative competence is not just a skill—it is a mindset, a habit of thought that enables teachers to lead classrooms where ideas flourish, problems are solved imaginatively, and language learning becomes a joyful, purposeful experience.

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ALISHER NAVOIY IJODINING ESTETIK TAMOYILLARINI O‘RGANISHGA DOIR

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Annotatsiya:Maqolada mutafakkir shoir Nizomiddin Mir Alisher Navoiyning ijodiy merosida inson hayoti va u yashayotgan jamiyat farovonligi borasida keltirilgan fikrlari bayon etilgan. Mutafakkir shoir Sharqda kechayotgan romantizm sharoitida o‘zini o‘ylantirgan masalalar xususida faqat badiiy so‘z va timsollar vositasida fikr-mulohazalarini bildiradi. U o‘zining o‘lmas asarlarida g‘oyaviy qarashlarini bir tizimga solib, inson kamoloti va jamiyat taraqqiyoti haqida aniq, kontseptual, dasturiy xulosalarini ifoda etadi.

Tayanch iboralar: inson kamoloti, mehr-shafqat, shaxs erkinligi, vatan, jamiyat, dunyo, vatan, tamoyil, ijod.

Vatanimizning uzoq tarixidan bu kunga qadar dunyo fani va madaniyati rivojiga katta hissa qo‘shgan donishmand allomalar o‘tishganki, ularning soni va salohiyati darajasini boshqa bir xalq tarixi misolida ko‘rish mushkul bo‘lsa kerak. Ular orasidagi yorqin tarixiy shaxsiyatlardan biri Nizomiddin Mir Alisher Navoiy edi. Mutafakkir shoir va yirik davlat arbobi Alisher Navoiy o‘z davri siyosiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy-ma’rifiy hayotini boshqarib turgan kuchlardan biri edi. Shu boisdan u davlat siyosati va jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalarini chuqur bilar, insonlar maishiy turmushlarida sodir bo‘layotgan muammolarni ham tushunar, daho ijodkor sifatida davlati va jamiyati taqdiriga befarq bo‘la olmas edi. Shoir o‘rta asrlarda Sharqda kechayotgan romantizm sharoitida o‘zini o‘ylantirgan masalalar xususida faqat badiiy so‘z va timsollar vositasida fikr-mulohazalarini bildirishi mumkin edi. Shu boisdan u o‘zining o‘lmas asarlarida nafaqat katta ko‘lamdagi masalalar, balki jamiyat kishisining har bir muammosi va qiziqishlari haqida aniq, kontseptual, dasturiy xulosalarini ifoda etadi.[2.25 b.]

Alisher Navoiy o‘z umri va ijtimoiy jamiyat hayotiga nazar tashlar ekan, muvaqqat hayot inson uchun faqat baxt manbaidangina iborat emasligini idrok etadi. Shu boisdan muvaqqat jamiyat hayotida faqat halol mehnat, pok niyat, qanoat, sabr kabi fazilatlar vositasida insonni yaxshi axloq va ibratli hayotga tashviq etadi. Uning bunday fikrlari ijtimoiy ruhdagi she’rlarida o‘z aksini topgan.[4, 145 b.]

Alisher Navoiyning qarashlariga ko‘ra, Tangri taolo yaratgan narsalar ichida eng sharafli insondir. Inson o‘ziga nasib etilgan umrni behuda emas, balki ongli va samarali kechirishi lozim. Navoiy o‘lmas she’riyatida dunyo, bashariyat hayoti, inson shaxsi xususida g‘oyatda badiiy fikr yuritadi. U insoniyat uchun eng muhim bo‘lgan masala – shaxs erkinligi

masalasini bir necha yo‘nalish bo‘yicha ta’riflab beradi. Navoiy inson qadri-qimmatini, uning yaratguchi tomonidan sharaflanganligini, oliy xilqat ekanligini birgina baytida ham, «Farhod va Shirin», «Saddi Iskandariy» kabi katta dostonlarida ham yorqin ifodalab beradi. Bir g‘azalida shoir ipak qafasda turgan erksiz qush timsolini tasvirlaydi:

Qushqa yung maskan aro xushroqdurur ozodliq,
Bo‘lg‘onidin band aro sayyod ipak domi bila. [3,76 b.]

Bu timsol vatangadolik, bewatanlikni anglatadi. Erkinlik shaxsning o‘z vatanida qo‘lga kiritiladi, inson o‘z sevimli maskanidan chekkada haqiqiy erkin bo‘la olmaydi.

Birovning qo‘li bilan insonga “hayvon sharbati”, ya’ni “abadiy hayot suvi”ning ichirilishi misoli esa yot g‘oyalarga qul bo‘lishni anglatadi. Shaxsiy manfaatini ko‘zlab begona qo‘l tutqizgan abadiy hayot suvini ichgandan ko‘ra, inson o‘z qo‘li bilan ajal sharbati – zaharni ichgani yaxshiroq:

Zahrni o‘z komi birla ichsa andin yaxshikim,
Ichsa hayvon sharbatin nokomliq jomi bila. [3,76 b.]

Xalq tabiatiga yot bo‘lgan begona mafkuraviy tazyiq yoki ongsiz ravishda ommaviy madaniyatga tobe‘lik insonni erkinlikdan mahrum etar ekan. Shoir inson ma’naviy dunyosi pokligiga va go‘zalligiga alohida e’tibor qaratadi. U pok va sadoqatli insoniy muhabbat tarafdori. Oshiqlar dillarini rom aylovchi yuzlab go‘zallar bo‘lgan bog‘larda yurgandan ko‘ra, inson o‘zining oddiygina maskanida ko‘ngliga orom beruvchi yagona yori bilan bo‘lgani afzaldir:

Yuz dilorom aylagandin ravza hibsi yaxshiroq,
Bo‘lmoq o‘z vayroni ichra ko‘ngli oromi bila. [3,76 b.]

Ammo, masalaning yana bir muhim tomoni ham borki, u ham bo‘lsa shaxs ozodligi faqat ijtimoiy, siyosiy yoki iqtisodiy jihatdan birovga mute’ bo‘lmaslikdagina emas ekan. Shaxs komil erkin bo‘lishi uchun o‘zini ma’nan - ruhan poklashi, ijtimoiy va maishiy hayotda ko‘zga tashlangan barcha salbiy xususiyatlardan nafratlanishi, doimo hamma sohalarda adolat, haqiqat sari intilishi lozim. Asosiysi, inson jismini o‘rgimchak iplaridek mahkam chirmab turgan yomon nafslardan – nafsni ammoradan faqat o‘z kuchi va xohishi bilangina qutulishga erishmog‘i lozim. Shoir o‘z nafsini yenga olmagan tama’gir insondan uyasida yotgan itni afzal ko‘radi:

Bo‘lmoq itlar mun‘imi tan to‘ma aylab yaxshiroq,
Tanni qilg‘uncha samin nokaslar in‘omi bila.[5,201 b.]

Insonlik sha’ni oqlamaganlarning sovg‘a-salomlari bilan samin liboslar kiyib, bezanib yurgandan ko‘ra, uyasida yotgan itga hamtovoq bo‘lgan yaxshiroqdir.

Koinot gultoji bo‘lmish insonni sevgan va ulug‘lagan buyuk mutafakkir Alisher Navoiy hazratlari shu boisdan ham o‘zlarining boshlariga tosh yog‘ilsa sabr qilib, elga qarata gul yaprog‘i otilsa, toqat qilolmaydilar, elga jafod qilinsa faryod uradilar:

Yuz jafod qilsa manga bir qatla faryod aylamon,
Elga qilsa bir jafod yuz qatla faryod aylaram; [3,7 b.]

Badkirdor insonlarning ko‘nglim sari otgan tig‘lari unga kor etmadi, elim qalbiga urgan tig‘lari esa mening ko‘nglimni behad vayron ayladi:

Tiyg‘i bedodi agar ko‘nglumni nokor etdi, lek,
Elga urg‘on tiyg‘i behad ko‘ngluma kor ayladi; [3,77 b.]

Quyidagi satrlarda insonsevar, insonparvar, insonshunos buyuk Navoiyning asl fitrati, nurli siymosi ayniqsa yorqin namoyon bo‘ladi:

Shikva qilmon gar jafodin boshima yog‘dursa tosh,
Toqatim yo‘q elga qilsa bargi gul urmoq havas. [3,77 b.]

Tosh va gul bargi tazodi bilan ulug‘ shoir oddiy insonga bo‘lgan muhabbatini ifoda etmoqda.

Xullas, Hazrat Alisher Navoiyning ulug‘ligi shundaki, u butun ijodida INSON haqida, uning ulug‘ligi va mukarramligi haqida fikr yuritadi. Bu fikr doirasi esa har qanday milliy, diniy, mazhabiy, mafkuraviy hududlarni yorib chiqadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan uning har bitta bayti katta umuminsoniy ahamiyat kasb etadi:

To g‘amdadur Navoiy, dahr anga tiyradur,

Shod anglamas ulusni birov bo‘lsa qayg‘uliy [1,150 b.].

Elimizning haqiqiy bebaho mulki bo‘lgan Alisher Navoiy hazratlarining tafakkur ummonlaridan qonib-qonib ichish va kun sayin, yil sayin, asrlar sayin unday to‘ymaslik, qonmaslik ehtiyoji oshib boraverishini umid qilaman.

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XX ASR ADABIYOTINI O‘RGANILISHIGA DOIR MULOHAZALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada XX asr o‘zbek adabiyotining o‘rganilishiga oid ayrim masalalar tahlil qilinadi. Unda Abdulla Qodiriy, G‘afur G‘ulom, Abdulla Qahhor kabi adiblarning murakkab davr sharoitida yaratgan asarlari, ularning ijodiy jasorati hamda mafkuraviy tazyiqlarga qarshi kurashi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, Abdulla Qahhorning “Yoshlar bilan suhbat” asarining tarixiy ahamiyati, adibning yosh iste’dodlarga bo‘lgan e’tibori va ularning shakllanishidagi o‘rni haqida fikr yuritiladi. Maqola istiqloq davrida milliy adabiyotimizni haqqoniy o‘rganish imkoniyatlari va ijodkorlarga bo‘lgan e’tiborning ortganini ham ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: XX asr adabiyoti, Abdulla Qahhor, ijodiy jasorat, “Yoshlar bilan suhbat”, adabiy tanqid, yosh iste’dodlar, istiqloq davri adabiyoti.

Annotation: This article presents reflections on the study of 20th-century Uzbek literature, focusing on the creative legacy and historical significance of prominent writers such as Abdulla Qodiriy and Abdulla Qahhor. It examines how the social and political environment of their time influenced their works and explores the impact of ideology and censorship on literary creativity. Special attention is given to Abdulla Qahhor’s moral

courage, critical thinking, and his mentorship of young writers. The article also highlights the post-independence revival of interest in national literary heritage, including the re-publication of Qahhor's works, such as *"Conversation with Youth"*, which remain valuable for understanding artistic truth, freedom of expression, and the development of modern Uzbek literature.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, Abdulla Qahhor, 20th century, censorship, ideology, literary criticism, creative freedom, young writers, independence, cultural revival.

Ma'lumki, har bir iste'dodli san'atkor o'z davrining farzandi sifatida ijod qiladi, tabiiyki, uning asarlarida o'sha davr muhitining ob'ektiv ta'siri u yoki bu tarzda aks etadi. XX asr adabiyotimiz vakillari, xususan, Abdulla Qodiriy va Qahhor ijodi ham o'z davr-muhitining ijtimoiy - siyosiy muammolari ta'siridan, xususan, hukmron mafkura iskanjasidan butunlay xolis bo'lishi mumkin emas edi. Zero, Qodiriy va Qahhorlar "hayot haqiqati va badiiy haqiqatga nechog'li katta e'tibor bermasin, tuzum va mafkura ba'zan ularni chekinishga majbur ham qilgan"ini (B.Nazarov) unutmash lozim. Ular ham og'ir zamonda yashadi. Haq so'zi uchun ne-ne ziyolilarga "xalq dushmani" degan tamg'a yopishtirilib, o'limga mahkum etilgani, millatning eng sara gullari "millatchi" degan tuhmat bilan mahv etilganini ko'rdi. Turli siyosiy ayblov-tazyiqlar, quruq tuhmatlar ularni ham chetlab o'tmadi. Qodiriy va Cho'lponlar qatori Qahhor kabi ulug' adiblarimizga hamisha yuksak e'tiqod va ehtirom ko'rsatib kelgan O'zbekiston Qahramoni Abdulla Oripov ular ko'rgan nohaqligini fojialarning asl sabab-oqibati haqida armon bilan mushohada yuritib, jumladan, G'.G'ulom ijodi va qiyin qismati haqida shunday yozadi: "Ular g'oyat murakkab, g'oyat ziddiyatli, tahlakali bir davrda yashab o'tdi. Mustabid imperiyaning beomon mafkurasi, mustamlakachilik siyosati minglab haqgo'ylar boshini yeyishga ulgurdi, qanchadan-qancha iste'dod egalarining bo'yniga bo'yun turuq solishga erishdi. Nog'orasiga o'ynashni xohlamaganlarni qatl qildi, quvg'in ostiga oldi. Shu tariqa o'zbek xalqi o'zining o'nlab beqiyos farzandlaridan bevaqt ayrildi. Madhiyabozlik adabiyotning ommaviy taom iliga aylangan. Ne-ne go'zal tashbehlar, chaqmoqdek misralar somon orasi dagi qahrabo bug'doy donalaridek nazardan qolib ketar edi. Ushbu achchiq haqiqatni, ayniqsa, bugungi yoshlar teran tushunmoqliklari kerak." Shunda ular Erk va Mustaqilligimizga qancha qurbonlar eaziga erishilganini chuqurroq anglab, uni qadrlashni o'rganadilar.

Istiqloldan so'ng xalqimizning ko'p asrli boy madaniyati va adabiyotini keng va haqqoniy o'rganishga beqiyos imkoniyatlar yaratildi. Jumladan, Abdulla Qahhor tavalludining 100 va 110 yilligi munosabati bilan qator asarlari qayta nashr etilishi ma'naviy va adabiy hayotimizdagi muhim bir voqea bo'ldi. O'z davrida qizg'in bahs-munozaralarga sabab bo'lgan "Sarob" romani va qissalarining ilmiy-tanqidiy matnlari bilan birga qaytadan nashr etilganligi tanqid va adabiyotshunos ligimiz uchun ham qimmatli manba bo'lib xizmat qilishi shubhasizdir.* Oldingi nashrlarida birmuncha qisqar tirib bosilgan yoki kiritilmay qolgan qator asarlari ham yangi nashrni tayyorlovchilar va tahririyat tomonidan e'tiborga olinganligi quvonarli holdir. Bu borada etuk matnshunos-adabiyotshunos Otabek Jo'raboev, Marhabo Qo'chqorova, Nodira Jalilova va Sanobar Matlubovalarning fidoyiliklarini ham qayd etish lozim. Ularning jonkuyarligi natijasida adibning bundan yarim asr muqaddam mustabid tuzum mafkurasi tomonidan butunlay qoralanib, badnom qilingan "**Yoshlar bilan suhbat**" asari ham ilk marta arxiv materiallari va qo'lyozmalari asosida alohida nashr etilishi tahsinga loyiqdir. "Insonni jisman yo'qotish mumkin, ammo uni engib bo'lmaydi" (Ernest Xemenguey) degan so'zlarni buyuk adiblarimizga va ular ning mumtoz asarlariga nisbatan ham aytish mumkin. Darhaqiqat, "qo'lyozmalar yonmaydi" deganlaridek, hayotiy haqiqat bilan yo'g'rilgan va xalqqa, adabiyot rivojiga xizmat qilishdek ulug' maqsad va ezgu niyatlar bilan yaratilgan asarlar yo'qolmaydi, mahv etilmaydi. O'zining betakror shaxsi, mardona haqgo'yiligi va jasorati, ko'rkam ijodi bilan adabiyotimiz tarixida o'chmas nom qoldirgan

realist adib Abdulla Qahhor asarlari bu jihatdan alohida e'tiborga loyiq. Xususan, adibning o'z davrida adabiyotimiz va tanqidchiligimiz saviyasini ko'tarishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan va hukmron sovet mafkurasining zo'ravonlik siyosatiga qarshi bir isyon bo'lib tuyulgan **"Yoshlar bilan suhbat"** kitobi bugun ham ijtimoiy adolatning yorqin bir dalili va unutilmas sabog'i bo'la oladi. Adib vafotidan so'ng zukko matnshunos va tarjimon Kibriyo Qahhorova hamda taniqli adabiyotshunoslar Ozod Sharafid dinov va Matyoqub Qo'shjonovlarning sa'y-harakati bilan 1968 yili chop etilgan **"Yoshlar bilan suhbat"*** kitobining nashri va bu noyob kitobning ayanchli taqdiridan bugungi minglab yosh kitobxonlarimiz deyarli bexabar deyish mumkin. 30 ming nusxada chop etilgan va adabiyotning ijtimoiy-estetik mohiyati, badiiy ijod va mahorat sirlaridan bahs etuvchi bu nodir kitob qahhorona keskin aytilgan fikrlar sababli savdo rastalaridan yig'ishtirib olinib, barchasi uyum-uyum qilib, nash riyot maydonida yoqib yuborilgan* Jaholatning chirkin namoyishi bo'lgan bu qabohat sababi haqida buyuk adabiyotshunos, O'zbekiston Qahramoni Ozod Sharafiddinovning **"Ijodni anglash baxti"** nomli asarida shikasta xotiralarni o'qiymiz:"1967 yil. Sentyabr oyining so'lim oqshomlaridan biri. Alisher Navoiy nomidagi teatr. Adibning 60 yillik to'yi nishonlanmoqda...Zalni liq to'ldirgan odamlar Abdulla Qahhorning nutqini kutish yapti. Nihoyat, unga so'z berildi... Nutq juda qisqa edi, lekin shu qisqa nutq zalda bo'ron yasadi. Ko'p o'tmay, bu bo'ron shaharga, viloyatga, butun respublikaga yoyildi. O'sha nda adib nima degan ediki, bu gaplar hammani bu qadar larzaga solgan edi. **"Men partiyaning soldati emas, ongli a'zosiman!"** Bu gap zalda bombaday portladi. Adibning Toshkentda kechasi aytgan gapi yarim soatda Moskvaga- Markaziy Komitetga va boshqa tashkilotlarga etgan edi. O'sha kezlarda va undan keyin ham butun Sovet Ittifoqida boshqa bironta yozuvchi buyruqni so'zsiz bajaradigan itoatkor soldat bo'lish g'oyasiga qarshi lom-lim degani yo'q. Abdulla Qahhor o'sha nutqida, aslida, inson erkini, inson aqlini himoya qilib hayqirgan, inson ustidan zo'ravonlik qilishga qarshi norozilik bildirgan edi...Abdulla Qahhor bu nutqidan keyin umrining oxirigacha va vafotidan keyin ham anchagacha ta'na-dashnomlardan qutulmadi..."* Bu achchiq haqiqatga qo'shimcha qilib aytish lozimki, hukmron kommunist ik firqaning ulug' adib ijodi va shaxsiga nisbatan adolatsizligi shu bil angina tugagani yo'q. Adabiyotimiz rivojiga beqiyos hissa qo'shgan xalq yozuvchisining ijodini o'rganish ancha yillar deyarli taqiqlab qo'yildi va adibning 70-75 yilliklari ham munosib nishonlanamadi, hatto adibga yaqin bo'lgan talantli shoir-yozuvchilar va adabiyotshunoslar ham u yoki bu yo'llar bilan tazyiqqa duchor qilindi. Aslida, bu nohaqliklarning tub sababi- Abdulla Qahhorning haqgo'yiligi va o'ziga xos ijodiy jasorati bilan bog'liq ediki, ko'p yoshlarimiz bu haqiqatni endi anglab etmoqda. Yoxud A.Qahhorning 1956 yili O'zbekiston Yozuvchilari uyushmasining Plenumida so'zlagan tarixiy nutqi hamda O'z Fanlar Akademiyasida Abdulla Qodiriyga bag'ishlangan yig'indagi (1964) ma'ruzasi qanchalik jiddiy ahamiyat kasb etganligi ham endilikda ayon bo'lmoqda. Qahhorning mantiqan boy, samimiyat to'la nutqlari nohaq qoralangan va stalincha mash'um siyosatning qurboni bo'lgan adiblarimizning hayoti va ijodini o'rganish va ular merosini xalqqa qaytarishdek dolzarb ishga botinolmay turgan ko'plab diyonatli olim va tadqiqotchilar uchun kuchli bir ma'naviy-ruhiy dalda bo'lganligi tarixiy haqiqatdir* O'zini adabiyotimizning "sergak posboni" deb bilgan Abdulla Qahhor kabi jasoratli adiblarimizning bunday yorqin nutq va maqolalari nafaqat badiiy ijod va adabiy-estetik tafakkurimiz rivojida, balki butun ijtimoiy-siyosiy va ma'naviy hayotimizda ham ulkan voqea bo'lganligi bilan ibratlidir. Adibning **"Yoshlar bilan suhbat"** asaridagi maqola, taqriz va qaydlarni ham o'qir ekanmiz, shunday bir xulosaga kelamiz: Adabiyot va ma'naviy hayotimizning bironta dolzarb muammosi yo'qki, u haqda Abdulla Qahhor o'z so'zini aytmagan bo'lsin. Chunonchi, adabiyotimiz kelajagi va uni yarat uvchi talantli yoshlar haqida g'amxo'rlik, badiiy ijod taraqqiyotining muhim omili bo'lgan mumtoz yozuvchilarning asarlari ni qunt bilan o'rganish, ularning go'zallik "sir"larini kashf etish, milliylik va baynalmilallik, badiiy til

muammolari. Yoxud ijod jarayoni, ijodkor shaxsi, ma'naviy qiyofasi, tanqid va adabiyotshunosligim izda mahorat masalala rining o'rganilishi... Ko'rinadiki, adabiy- tarixiy jarayonning asosiy yo'nalishlarini belgilovchi va Qahhor uchun ham g'oyat ahamiyatli bo'lgan muammolarni loaqal sanab ko'rsatish uchun ham butun bir sahifa etmaydi. Shuning uchun bu o'rinda ana shu muhim muammolardan ayrim lari haqida- ushbu yangi nashrda ham ancha keng yoritilgan mavzu –Abdulla Qahhorning ijodkor yoshlarga munosabati xususida va adibning yon daftarlari borasida muxtasar fikr yuritiladi. Abdulla Qahhor ijodi va shaxsini ozmi-ko'pmi o'rgangan va xususan, adib shogirdlari va zamondoshlarining yorqin xotiralari bilan yaqindan tanishgan kishi shunday bir xulosaga kelishi tabiiy: hozirgi zamon o'zbek adabiyotimizda iste' dodli yoshlar tarbiya siga Abdulla Qahhorchalik mehnati ko'p singgan, yoshlar ijodi va ma'naviy intellektual saviyasini Qahhor darajasida chuqur o'rgangan va ularga bu qadar kuchli ta'sir o'tkaza olgan yirik san'atkor o'tmagan desak, mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Shukur Xolmirzaev havas va hayrat bilan aytganidek, adib bu jihatdan “istisno shaxs” edi. Adabiyot maydoniga kirib kelayotgan va “qalamni shuhrat yoki boshqa narsa ta'ma qilib emas, balki qalbidagi muhabbat va nafrat olovini olamga sochish” uchun olgan hech bir yosh ijodkor Abdulla Qahhorning o'tkir nigoxidan chetda qolmas edi. Dastlabki asarlari bilanoq ustoz adib nazariga tushgan, undan ruhiy madad olgan va endilikda o'zlari ham ijodiy kamolot darajasiga ko'tarilib, adabiyot imizning zalvorli yukini o'z zimmalariga olgan etuk ijodkorlarimiz ozmuncha emas. Qahhorning bu boradagi ibratli faoliyati adabiyotimiz rivoji uchun naqadar katta ahami yatga ega bo'lganligi va adib o'zining butun ijodi va mazmunli umri bilan yoshlarga qanday munosabatda bo'lish sabog'ini qoldirganligi, ayniqsa, Erkin Vohidovning “Qarzdorlik” nomli xotir asida ajib bir teranlik bilan ifodalangan: “Abdulla Qahhor biz endi adabiyotga qadam qo'ygan davr muhitining marka zida turgan shaxs edi, yoshlarga alohida e'tiborli, iste'dodni ilg'ash qobili yati beni hoya kuch li ustoz edi. Said Ahmad, M.Qo'shjonov, O.Sharafiddinov, O. Yoqubov, P.Qodirov, O'.Umarbekov, A.Oripov, O'.Hoshimov, Sh.Xolmirzaev, U.Nazarov singari yozuvchi larning ijodiy taqdirida A.Qahhorning ustozlik o'rni bor. Ustozning menga, so'ngra A.Oripovga ko'rsatgan xayrixohligi biz uchun o'ziga xos yashinqaytar gichday bo'lgani sir emas”. **Erkin Vohidov. Qarzdorlik.- Iztirob. T, 1992, 239-b.** Yuqoridagi ro'yxatni Qahhor ijodidan va badiiy mahurat saboqlaridan bahramand bo'lgan Tog'ay Murod, Xayrididdin Sulton, Erkin A'zam, SHoyim Bo'ta yev kabi o'nlab iste'dodli adiblarimiz bilan davom ettirish mumkin. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, talantli yoshlarga doimiy e'tibor va g'amxo'rlik A.Qahhorning tabiatiga xos bo'lgan fazilatlardan edi. Bu haqda adibning o'zi yon daftarida shunday deydi:“Yozuvchi adabiyotga ikki xil kiradi: birinchi asari bilan tutab, birinchi asari bilan yashnab kiradi...Men adabiyot muhibiman, shuning uchun adabiyotga yashnab kirgan yoshlarni ko'rib quvonib ketaman, quvonchimni o'sha yoshning o'ziga izhor qilib aytaman.Bu yashnagan cho'g'ni elpish demakdir”. (Asarlar, 6-t.,470-b.)“Adabiyot muhibi”-qahhorona kamtarinlik bilan aytilgan oddiygina ibora. Lekin shu oddiy so'zlar zamirida qanchalar mas'uliyat va jo'mardlik mujassam. Abdulla Qahhor ning iste'dodli yoshlarga ko'rsatgan mehr-e'tibori haqida o'ylaganda, beixtiyor benazir siymo, adabiyot va ilmu fazl ahliga tengsiz homiy Navoiy bilan ulug' adib Maksim Gorkiy yodimizga keladi. K.Fedinning guvohlik berishicha, har bir yosh iste'dodning adabiyot maydoniga kirib kelishi M.Gorkiyni shu qadar quvontirar ekanki, u o'sha ”yosh ijodkorning yo'liga bamisoli poyon doz bo'lib to'shalgisi kelar, toki u ortiqcha mashaqqat va to'siqlarga behuda kuch sarf qilmay ijodning yuksak cho'qqilari tomon tezroq ko'tarila olsin”,- der ekan. Darhaqiqat, talantni- xalqning bebaho mulki deb bilgan Abdulla Qahhorning iste' dodli yoshlarga g'amxo'rlik va homiyliigi ham hayratangiz edi. Zotan, uning adabiyotga va ijod axliga jonkuyarligi, ayniqsa, iste'dodli yosh larga talabchan murabbiyligi, eng avvalo, bu ulkan ijodkor qalbining oliyhimmatliligi va oliyjanoblighi bilan, adabiyotimiz va manaviyatimiz ravnaqi yo'lidagi fidoiy jonkuyarligi

va masuliyati bilan izohlanadi. Qahhorning yoshlar haqidagi maqola va nutqlari dastavval shunisi bilan diqqatga molikki, ularda ko‘plab yosh shoir va yozuvchilar ijodiga xos bo‘lgan eng muhim fazilatlar nuqtadonlik bilan e‘tirof etilar hamda ularning asarlaridagi nuqsonlar va ijodiy o‘sishiga xalaqit berayotgan muammolar ham aniq-tiniq ko‘ratib berilar edi. Shu jihatlari bilan ular tanqid va adabiyotshunosligimizda yosh iste‘dodlar ijodi haqida yaratilajak tadqiqotlarning yorqin bir sahifasi bo‘lib qolishi shubhasiz. Abdulla Qahhor adabiy yoshlarning asarlarini o‘ziga xos sinchi kovlik va talabchanlik bilan muttasil kuzatib va tahlil etib borar ekan, ularning ijodiy imkoniyatlari va intellektual salohiyatlarini yuksak qadrlar edi. Xususan, ustoz adib imizning 1965 yili yosh ijodkorlar bilan o‘tkazgan suhbat adabiyotimiz va tanqidchiligimiz tarixida ham unutilmas uchrashuvlardan bo‘lib qolishini o‘shanda hamma ham birdek tasavvur etolmagan bo‘lsa kerak. “Hozirgi adabiyotimiz,- degan edi Qahhor o‘sha suhbatda,- naqadar yaxshi, naqadar katta bo‘lmasin, kelajakda yaratiladigan buyuk o‘zbek adabiyotining poydevori, faqat poydevori bo‘lib qoladi. Men nima uchun ertaga buyuk adabiyot yaratilishiga, bu adabiyotni hozirgi yoshlar yaratishiga aminman? Men hozirgi yoshlarni o‘zimning yoshligimga, bularning dastlabki asarlarini o‘zimning dastlabki asarlarimga qiyos qilib, shunday ishonch paydo qildim”. Hayot Abdulla Qahhorning bashoratini ro‘yobga chiqardi- bugungi kunda, eng avvalo, Istiqlol sharofati bilan o‘zbek adabiyoti va tanqidchiligi ham g‘oyaviy, ham badiiy-estetik saviyasi jihatidan yangi bir bosqichga ko‘tarildi. Shu munosabat bilan Abdulla Qahhor uy-muzeyidagi an‘anaviy xotira kechasida aytilgan muhim bir haqiqatni alohida ta’kidlash lozim. Taniqli adiblar va akademiklarimiz A.Qayumov, B.Nazarov, N.Karimovlar hamda ustozlar U.Normatov, I.G‘afurov bilan birga X.Do‘stmuhammad, S.Umirov, A.Meliboev, Q.Yo‘ldo shev, Sh.Rizaev, R.Qo‘chqorov va Farg‘onadan Y.Solijonov, Gulistondan U.O‘ljaboev, Jizzaxdan bir necha adabiyotshunoslar qatnashgan o‘sha anjumanda sharqona lutf va minnatdorlik bilan tarixiy bir voqea e‘tirof etilgan edi. Ya’ni Istiqlol davrida adabiyotga munosabat tubdan o‘zgardi, ijod ahliga ishonch-e‘tibor va g‘amxo‘rlik har qachongidan ortdi. Buning yorqin dalili- bir necha zabardast ijodkorlarimiz-Said Ahmad, Abdulla Oripov, Erkin Vohidov, Ozod Sharafiddinov va keyinroq To‘lapbergen Qayipbergenovlar Vatanimizning yuksak mukofoti - O‘zbekiston Qahramoni unvoni bilan taqdirlandi. Quvonchli tomoni yana shundaki, ularning barchasi Qahhorning mehr-shafoatidan va unutilmas saboqlaridan bahramand bo‘lganlar. Shu boisdan ham biz bugun ustozimiz Abdulla Qahhorni to‘rt marta adabiyotimiz Qahramoni bo‘ldi,- deb e‘zozlaymiz.

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РЕАЛИИ ВОСТОКА В ПОВЕСТИ «ХАДЖИ-МУРАД» Л.Н. ТОЛСТОГО

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Аннотация. В повести Л.Н. Толстого «Хаджи-Мурад» реалии Востока показаны через описание быта, традиций, культуры и религиозных верований горцев Кавказа, а также через их взаимоотношения с русской администрацией Кавказской войны. Писатель фокусируется на таких аспектах, как мусульманская культура, исламские традиции, этика горцев, их суровый образ жизни в горах и конфликты между различными племенами.

Главным героем одноимённой повести Л.Н. Толстого является аварец, исповедующий ислам. События описанные в произведении происходят в 1851 – 1852 годы, когда Л. Н. Толстой находился на Кавказе. Здесь писатель узнал о подвигах молодого горца боровшегося за сохранение своей чести, своей родины. История молодого кавказца сильно заинтересовала художника. В результате, писатель стал внимательно изучать историю Кавказской войны эпохи Николая и хронику сопротивления горных народов северного Кавказа. Он собирал архивные документы, расспрашивал участников разыгрывающихся событий, беседовал с документалистами, осведомлёнными о происшедших историях, беседовал с горцами, солдатами и офицерами, изучал тюркские слова, выражения и записывал их, которые впоследствии пригодились в создании целостных образов.

После долгой подготовительной работы мастер слова приступил к написанию повести в 1896 году. Не доставало многого, поэтому пришлось работать над текстом с перерывами и только в конце 1904 года великий художник смог завершить своё повествование о Хаджи – Мурате.

В книге отражены, драматичные военные действия, не до конца решённые вопросы крепостничества, порабощение горцев, доведённые до отчаяния. Поднятые в повести вопросы могли быть урезаны жёсткой цензурой, может быть поэтому, он и не решался издать книгу до своей смерти.

Повесть была издана через два года после кончины автора его другом, писателем и издателем В.Г. Черновым в 1912 году в Москве, и вошла в третий том «Посмертных художественных произведений Л. Н. Толстого».

В экспозиции повести описана середина лета, на полях были убраны луга, собирались косить рожь. С самого начала повествования автор широко использует приём контраста. Полевые цветы радовали глаза. Рассказчик, возвращаясь домой из прогулки, набрал большой букет нежных летних цветов, отдающих медовыми и миндальными запахами. А рядом с цветами в канаве росла репей, в полном цвету, которое местное население называли, «татаринном» и осторожно скашивали их, а когда случайно окашивали, выделяли из сена и выбрасывали, чтобы не колоть об неё руку. И решил повествователь украсить середину букета этими цветами. Природа жила своей жизнью, и согнав впившегося в середину цветка шмеля, он принялся срывать стебель цветка, а он не поддавался, кололся и сопротивлялся, а когда был сорван, потерял былую форму и превратился в лохмотья. Выбросив цветок, он задумался, пожалел о своём поступке. Его удивила сила татарина, его старание выстоять, выжить и он про себя подумал: «Как он усиленно защищал и дорого продал свою жизнь». [1] Пыльная дорога на два разделяла большое, аккуратно вспаханное чернозёмное поле, не было видно ни одного живого растения или цветка, и опять он задумывается над жестокостью человека, способного уничтожать флору и фауну, нужную для

поддержания своей же жизни. Идя своей дорогой, он заметил куст, подойдя к нему, увидел, что он был переехан колёсами, один стебель был сломлен, цветы были в грязи, а сам татарин стоял, несколько склоняясь на бок. И он подумал, что человек уничтожил его братьев, полевых цветов, а он не сдался и стоит. Эти картины напомнили писателю знакомую историю жизни Хаджи – Мурата – героя одноимённой повести.

Автор в начале своей книги пишет: «И мне вспомнилось одна давнишняя кавказская история, часть которой я видел, часть слышал от очевидцев, а часть вообразил». [2] Как видим, Л. Н. Толстой в повести использовал наряду с документальными и доступными материалами, также и художественный вымысел, тем самым выполнив основное требование художественной литературы.

Центральное место в повести занимает – Хаджи-Мурат, главный герой повести. Он родился в небольшом селении Цельмес, недалеко от Царьграда – Хунхаза – где жили ханы. А его родители были в хороших отношениях с султанской семьёй. Случилось так, что его мать своей грудью кормила Абунунцала – старшего хана.

Хаджи – Мурат имел хороший слух от природы, с малых лет слушал песни своей матери, о защитниках родины, о подвигах джигита, перелётных птицах и задумывался. Много времени проводил он с матерью во дворце, вместе с ханами постепенно превратился в своего человека, и делал всё что хотел. У него были и богатство, и роскошь. Пройдут годы, забудется многое, но к песням, спетым матерью, он будет возвращаться многократно – они в той или иной форме будут сопровождать его до самой его смерти. У хана были трое детей: Абунунцал – Хан, Умма – Хан и Булач – Хан, и все жили, не зная недостатков, весёлой жизнью.

А потом пришла беда – убили Кази – Муллу. Его место занял непредсказуемый Гамзат. Примерно с этого времени в горных аулах из уст его сторонников чаще стали звучать призывы к священной войне с неверными. Гамзат прислал к ханам своих послов с требованием участвовать в вооружённом сопротивлении и предупреждал их что, если не примут участие в борьбе с неверными, то он разорит их столицу. А ханы были молоды и не закалённые в военных сражениях, боялись русских и Гамзата. В их глазах в сторону последнего переходили тысячи чеченцев и аварцы. Стремительно развивающиеся события пугали их. Обращение к главному русскому начальнику барону Розану Умма – Хана и сопровождавшего его Хаджи – Мурата не дали результатов, а наоборот разорило их. После такого отношения к ханам русских, оставалось единственное правильное решение принять требование Гамзата. Но имам не доверял ханам, и думал, что они помешают ему в борьбе против неверных, злонамеренно пообещав им верное служение, как служил бывшему Хану его отец, заманил к себе двух старших ханов и убил страшной, мучительной смертью. Здесь впервые рядом с имамом появляется Шамил. Свидетелем этой ужасной казни невольно стал сопровождавший их Хаджи – Мурат. Убив ханов, Гамзат переехал в Царьград, вошёл во дворец и занял трон. А между тем, оставался самый младший хан – его убил Шамил, сбросив с кручи. Имам пригласил к себе ханшу, а она стала выговаривать ему. Услышав её претензии, верный слуга Гамзата ударом меча убил её. Так было покончено с ханством. Вся Чечня и Авария подчинилась Иمامу. Главное требование имамата было борьба против неверных, только Хаджи – Мурат и его младший брат Осман не хотели покориться ему. Они были свидетелями многих жестокостей и убийств со стороны Гамзата и Шамиля, и горели желанием отомстить им. Братья в местной мечети убили имама, потеря была и со стороны братьев, был убит и Осман. Заняв место убитого Гамзата Шамил, отправил своих послов к Хаджи – Мурату с требованием присоединиться к его частям и идти против русских, иначе он грозился разорить Хунхаз

и убить его. А он не выполнил требования нового имама, посчитав его убийцей своего брата Османа и Абунунцал – хана.

А между тем, русский генерал Розен вёл свою политику, чтобы развести Шамиля и Хаджи – Мурата. Он присвоил последнему офицерский чин и приказал стать правителем Аварии. Дело было в том, что на это должность ранее он назначал Магамет – Мирзу, а за тем Ахмет – Хана. Воспользовавшись своим высоким положением, он, сватал своего сына на ханскую дочь Салтанет, а её не отдали. Тогда Ахмат – хан виною этому посчитав Хаджи – Мурата решил убить его, а он ушёл от его преследования. Всё же, Ахмат – хан многое наговорил генералу Клюгенау. По велению генерала задержали Хаджи - Мурата и решили этапировать в административный центр Темир - Хан – Шуру. Вели его связанными руками сорок солдат с заряженными винтовками. Пошли по горной тропинке, она была узкой, проходя по ней, он бросился в обрыв, потащив за собой солдата, находившегося рядом, который разбился на смерть, а он остался жив с многочисленными ушибами и переломами. С помощью добрых людей он восстановился, только хромота правой ноги ему напоминала об этом случае. После выздоровления он прибрался в родное селение Цельмес. Узнав об этом, аварцы уговаривали его управлять ими, а он согласился.

И имамат и русские генералы хотели увидеть Хаджи – Мурата на своей стороне. О чем свидетельствует два письма генерала Клюгенау с уговорами выйти к русским. А он не пошёл к русским, потому, что на их стороне был его злейший враг Ахмет – Хан, переходя к ним, он не смог бы отомстить ему.

К этому времени Цельмес был окружён Ахмат – ханом, целью которого было схватить или убить своего ненавистника. Защититься от него было сложно, по численности его сторонники в несколько раз превосходили защитников аула.

В это сложное для выбора время, прибыл к нему посланник от Шамиля с письмом, в котором было обещано помочь отбиться от Ахмат – Хана и дать ему управление над Аварией, если он перейдёт на его сторону. Выхода другого не было, и он перешёл на сторону Шамиля. Начиная с этого времени Хаджи - Мурат бился с русскими. Он отличался особой смелостью, решительностью, все его набеги и походы на противника увенчивались успехом, многие верили на его удачливость. Даже его враги удивлялись и поражались его смелыми нападениями и решениями в сложных ситуациях, поэтому и имам Шамил, и русские хотели, заманит его к себе. По известным причинам он перешёл к Шамилю и начал сотрудничать с ним.

Но это партнёрства продолжалась до тех пор, пока не задали ему каверзный вопрос о том, кто будет имамом после Шамиля и услышали в ответ что « ... имамом будет тот, у кого шашка востра». Сказанное передали имаму, а тот решил избавиться от недруга. Отправив своих людей, имам отобрал всё состояние Хаджи – Мурата и потребовал его явку к нему, что была равносильна смерти. Для исполнения воли хозяина пришли люди Шамиля, отбил его Хаджи – Мурат и в течение трёх бессонных ночей - безустанно убегал он со своими четырьмя мюридами от преследователей и в морозный ноябрьский вечер заехал в чеченский аул Махкет, и повернул в дом своего знакомого Садо. Над аулом прозвучал азан, призывающий к вечерней молитве. В доме гостей встретил старик, отец хозяина дома, известный пчеловод, который сразу узнал Хаджи – Мурата, предводителя горцев, известного своими подвигами. Брат хозяина дома Бота в позднюю ночь, повёл мюрида гостя к русским. Нужно было договориться, о встрече своего предводителя с полковым командиром Семёном Михайловичем Воронцовым - сыном главнокомандующего. Хаджи – Мурат всегда был уверен в своём успехе. Удача всегда сопутствовала ему.

Верил он, что и на этот раз будет так. «Он представлял себе, как он с войском, которое даст ему Воронцов, пойдёт на Шамиля и захватит его в плен, и отомстит ему, и как русский царь наградит его, и он опять будет управлять не только Аварией, но и всей Чечнёй, которая покорится ему. И их первая встреча состоялась на следующее утро на месте рубки. Свита Хаджи – Мурата состояло из четырёх человек - Хан – Магома, тавлинца Ханефи, заведующего его имуществом, молодого Элдара и Гамзало с рыжей бородой и шрамом поперёк лица. Хаджи – Мурат, подъехав близко к Воронцову Семёну Михайловичу, заявил о своём намерении служить русскому Царю вместе со своей свитой и они друг – другу пожали руки. Когда Воронцов и Хаджи – Мурат, сопровождающий их со своей свитой, направились к крепости, собравшиеся в кучки солдаты, с разных сторон признавали его подвиги, называя его молодчиной, джигитом, а другой, стоящий в стороне солдат вслух размышлял, и было слышно что «били его много раз. - Ну, да и от него доставалось».[3]

Хаджи – Мурат понял, что они говорили о нём, и улыбка выражалась в его глазах и губах. Воронцов был доволен, тем, что именно ему удалось завлечь важного лица из круга Имама Шамиля. С другой стороны, на душе было неприятно, командующим войсками в Воздвиженской был генерал Меллер – Закомельский, подобные переговоры должны были вестись через него. А Воронцов не о чём не предупредил генерала, выполнил всё сам, от чего могли выйти неприятности. Оставив Хаджи – Мурата дома, Воронцов направился в свою канцелярию, чтобы сделать распоряжение об извещении начальства о выходе Хаджи – Мурата. Написав донесение генералу Козловскому, начальнику левого фланга и письмо отцу, вернулся домой.

Воронцов у себя дома принял Хаджи – Мурата с достоинством и уважением. Подобный приём Воронцова несколько удивила Хаджи – Мурата. Он боялся, что его обманут, схватят и сошлют в Сибирь или просто убьют. Расспросив Элдара и узнав о том, что лошади в конюшне, а его людей поместили в сарае и оставили оружия при них, он немного успокоился.

Уладил Воронцов и с генералом Миллером, тот в свою очередь, пригласил к себе гостя, стал расспрашивать его. Хаджи – Мурат рассказал ему о том, что он вышел из гор, чтобы служить русскому царю и обо всём хочет рассказать главнокомандующему Воронцову в Тифлисе.

В объём сравнительно небольшой повести, Л. Н. Толстой вместил ёмкое содержание. Здесь описаны реальные военные противостояния Российской империи с северокавказскими горцами, видны человеконенавистническая идеология в политике Никола. Вопросы войны и мира, пьянство, армейские раздоры и жестокости, грабёж, себялюбие и глупости армейских командиров и генералов армии способствовавшие уничтожению горной природы, продовольственных ресурсов, уничтожению целых деревень, гибели своих солдат и мирного населения.

Так же, показаны жестокая борьба за власть, распри между разными слоями горцев, малограмотность, их убогая жизнь, объединение и борьба за сохранение родины во главе с имамом Шамилем.

Эти и другие полюсы в произведении расходятся и сходятся, создавая единые и целостные картины жизни вокруг Хаджи – Мурата, главного героя одноимённой повести. Жизнь героя, как и жизнь всех горцев, как говорили мы выше, протекала в сложную и противоречивую эпоху, когда на Кавказе шла жестокая, кровопролитная противостояния за власть между кланами. Сюда добавилась и политика раздела мира сильными государствами. Жёсткая политика Николаевской власти в этом вопросе

намного усложнила и без того противоречивую жизнь северокавказских народов, так в книге переплетаются несколько сюжетных линий.

Главнокомандующий Михаил Семёнович Воронцов, был сыном русского посла, воспитывался в Англии, выделялся от русских чиновников своим европейским образованием. Был он человек честолюбивый, ласковый и мягкий. Он не понимал жизнь без покорности и власти. Генерал имел все высшие чины, считался искусным воином, даже считался победителем Наполеона под Краоном. В 1851 – м году ему было 70 лет, но всё ещё был свеж и бодр, имел большое состояние, строил дворец на берегу Крыма. В начале декабря 1851 года вечером к его дворцу в Тифлисе подъехала тройка. Молодой офицер привёз ему от генерала Козловского письмо, где сообщалось о выходе Хаджи – Мурата к русским. Узнав об этом, Главнокомандующий, вернувшись в гостиную, приятным голосом стал рассказывать о выходе одного из храбрейших воинов Кавказа Хаджи – Мурата к русским. Это сообщение приятно удивило всех присутствующих. Из гостей, рыжий генерал с щетинистыми усами вспоминал, как в 43 Хаджи – Мурат со своим отрядом захватил Гергебиля и тогда он наткнулся с отрядом генерала Пассека и на глазах у всех чуть не убил полковника Золотухина. Тот же генерал вспомнил о даргинском походе, который возглавлял нынешний главнокомандующий Воронцов. Из засады напал на них со своим отрядом Хаджи – Мурат, со стороны русских было много убитых и раненных, погибли бы все в отряде, если бы не выручило вновь подошедшее войско. Сидевший за столом армянин вспомнил как в сорок девятом году, среди белого дня он ворвался в административный центр Темир – хан – Шуру и разграбил лавочные ряды. Участник застолья, грузинский князь утверждал, что родился он в Европе, стал бы новым Наполеоном. Один из участников рассказал, как Хаджи – Мурат похищал вдову Ахмат – хана, но с уважением относился к пленнице, а потом её отпустил за выкуп. Вспоминали и о других благородных поступках Хаджи – Мурата, а им числа не было. Один из участников вечера громко заметил: «Хаджи – Мурат вышел, теперь конец Шамилю...» [5] Старому генералу, участнику мировой войны, было лестно слушать эти рассказы о смелом человеке.

На другой день как было сообщено в письме сына к генералу, Хаджи – Мурат прибыл в Тифлиссский дворец главнокомандующего Воронцова. Генерал принял Хаджи – Мурата в просторном кабинете с большими окнами, стоя у края огромного стола, его старое лицо было серьёзное. Увидев русского генерала Хаджи – Мурат приложил свои руки к груди и почтительно заговорил на кумыкском языке, которым он владел и признался, что хочет отдаться и служить до конца жизни русскому Царю и ему. Так же он признавался, что хотел быть полезным в войне с Шамилем, своим врагом. Выслушав Хаджи – Мурата Воронцов взглянул в его глаза, а Хаджи – Мурат в лицо Воронцова. Взгляды эти без слов говорили о многом. Глаза главнокомандующего говорили что, он не верит ни одному слову Хаджи – Мурата, он враг всему русскому и останется им. А взгляд последнего говорил, что старику этому нужно бы думать о смерти, чем о войне, но про себя подумал, что старец этот хитёр, и нужно быть осторожным с ним. И генерал был уверен всё что, он сказал Хаджи – Мурату, нужна для успеха на войне. Гость так же через переводчика передал, что когда он управлял Аварией в 39 – м. году, верой и правдой служил русским, но его оклеветал Ахмат – Хан генералу Клюгенау. Ахмат – Хана и Шамиля он называл своими врагами, Первой из них уже умер, а второй ещё жив и обещал он отомстить ему. И он сказал: «... если его пошлют на лезгинскую линию и дадут ему войско, то он ручается, что поднимет весь Дагестан и Шамилю нельзя будет держаться.» [4]

На этой встрече Хаджи – Мурата беспокоили и другие вопросы, особенно вопросы его семьи. Убегая от своих преследователей Хаджи – Мурат не позаботился, о безопасности своей семьи, не вывез их из вражеской территории, что не давала ему покоя.

Его мать, жёны и дети всё ещё оставались на сопредельной территории врага. Поэтому, он просил генерала, чтобы он, выручил его близких, обменяв на военнопленных горцев. А после освобождения родных, он обещал вступить в смертный бой с Шамилем.

Двадцатого декабря того же года Генерал Воронцов отправил письмо на французском языке военному министру Чернышеву. В нём, главнокомандующий подробно сообщал о прибытии Хаджи – Мурата, в Тифлис, Который, по его мнению, являлся одним из влиятельных людей не только из окружения Шамиля, но и всего Кавказа. Так же он, сообщал Чернышеву о его трудном семейном положении, которая находилось в руках Шамиля. Говорилось в письме и о просьбах его, об обмене его семьи на военнопленных горцев. Так же он сообщал, что в случае успеха Хаджи – Мурат мог бы стать, самым полезным для исполнения поставленной цели государя. И просил он министра передать государю свою просьбу, учитывая условия и обстановку на фронте, оставить Хаджи - Мурата в пределах Грозного с 20 –ю казаками для его сопровождения. Донесение Воронцова было отправлено из Тифлиса 24 декабря. 1 января 1852 года в числе прочих документов военный министр и это письмо Воронцова повёз к императору Николаю.

Толстой, в своей повести особое внимание обращает раскрытию характеров власть имущих, начиная от самого императора, до его министров, генералов и чиновников: Чернышев не любил Воронцова, и за всеобщего к нему внимания, и уважения окружающих, за его огромное состояние, главное за особое расположение монарха к нему.

Исходя из всего вышесказанного, следует заметить, что в повести Л.Н. Толстого «Хаджи-Мурат» жизнь восточных людей показана через описание быта, традиций, культуры, религиозных верований жителей Кавказа. А также, изображается их взаимоотношение с русской дворянской общиной, во главе с генералами, командирами и армией. Толстой в своей повести показывает исламские традиции, мусульманскую культуру, суровую жизнь в горах Кавказа и конфликты между различными этносами.

ALISHER NAVOIY SHE'RIYATIDA QOSID OBRAZINING MOHIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada milliy mumtoz adabiyotimiz xususan, she'riyatida qosid timsoli qo'lanilishining ildizi, adabiyotimiz xazinasidan o'rin olgan she'riy asarlar muayyan bir sana bilan chegaralangan bo'lishiga qaramay, ancha uzoqlarga borib taqalishi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qosid, mumtoz, timsol, she'riyat, xabarchi, uyg'onish davri, lirik qahramon, she'riy asarlar.

Navoiy g'azaliyotining lirik qahramonlari haqida so'z ketganda, asosan, oshiq va ma'shuqa obrazlaritilga olinadi. Haqiqatdanham, shoirning ishqiy mavzudagi g'azallarida oshiq va ma'shuqaning turli holatlari yorqin bo'yoqlarda tasvirlangan. Adabiyotshunos olim A.Hayitmetov ta'kidlaganidek, "Navoiy ishqiy g'azallarining yarmidan ko'pi oshiqning ichki

kechinmalarini, uning hijron azoblarini, dard-alamlarini, orzu-armonlarinikuylashgabag'ishlangan" [1, 123-b].

Navoiyning dunyoqarashi, ijod va go'zallikka bo'lgan estetik munosabati, falsafiy va filologik qarashlari, poetik mahorati, ijodiy metodi va uslubi, adabiy muhit bilan aloqasi va uning shoir faoliyatiga ta'siri o'zbek va xorij olimlari tomonidan sermahsul o'rganilgan. E.E.Bertels, Oybek, S.Ayniy, M.Shayxzoda, A.Qayumov A.Hayitmetov, N.Mallayev, A.Rustamov. S.Erkinov, T.Jalolov, Y.Ishoqov, A.Valixonov, A.Shomuhamedov, A.Hojiahmedov, S.G'aniyeva, A.Mirzayev, S.Ivanov, Ali Asqar Hikmat, Rukniddin Humoyun Farrux, N.Komilov, I.Haqqul, M.Imomnazarov, M.Muhiddinov, Sh.Sirojiddinov, A.Erkinov, S.Olim kabi olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqotlari navoiyshunoslikka qo'shilgan bebaho hissadir.

Milliy mumtoz adabiyotimiz xususan, she'riyatimiz xazinasidagi manbalar o'rganilganida, qosid timsolini an'anaviy va azaliy timsollarsirasiga kiritish mumkinligiga amin bo'ldik.

Dastlab she'riyatimizda sabo biror gul hidini atrofga sochuvchi timsol vazifasini bajargan. Jumladan, Yusuf Xos Hojibning "Qutadg'u bilig" asarida shunday misralarni o'qiymiz:

***Saba eli qo'pti qaranful yidin,
Ajun barcha butru yipar burdi kin [2, 14-b].***

Tabdili: *Chinnigul hidini yoyarkan sabo,
Butun dunyo to'ldi iporga go'yo. (Bahor madhi)*

Garchi, manbalarda xabarchi timsoli aynan qosid nomi bilan aytilmasa-da, *hudhud, sabo, nasim, roviy* timsollari ham qosid vazifasini bajaradi, ya'ni lirik qahramon – oshiq o'zining ma'lum bir holatini ma'shuqasiga etkazish uchun yuqoridagi timsollarga murojaat etadi. Jumladan, Xorazmiyning "Muhabbatnoma" asarining ikkinchi nomasida quyidagi baytda nasim shunday vazifani bajaradigan timsol sifatida gavdalanadi;

***Salomim gulga elt, ey tong nasimi,
Kim erur Oy quli, Axtar nadimi [3, 18-b].***

Baytni tahlil qilishdan oldin undagi "axtar", "nadim" kabi tushunilishi qiyin so'zlar qatorida "nasim" so'zining ma'nosiga to'xtalamiz: buning uchun yana "Alisher Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati"ga murojaat qilamiz:

Nasim – tong shamoli, engil, yoqimli shabada.

Mazkur lug'atda "axtar" va "nadim" so'zlariga shunday ta'rif berilgan:

Axtar – 1.Yulduz. 2.Taqdir, qismat; baxt. 3.Yuz, jamol, chiroy, husn. 4.Bayroq, tug'. 5.Manzil, makon; shu'la.

Nadim – 1. Xizmatkor, mahram. 2. Yaqin do'st, hamsuhbat

Biz bu sharhlardan bayt mazmunidan kelib chiqib, har ikkala so'zning birinchi ma'nolarini olamiz. U holda baytda lirik qahramon – oshiqning tong shamoliga murojaati tasvirlangani oydinlashadi, ya'ni lirik qahramon tong shamolini Oy quli, Axtar nadimi (yulduz mahrami) deb sifatlab, undan o'z salomini gul – yorga etkazishini iltimos qilaypti. Unda nasim yorga xabar eltuvchi timsoli vazifasini bajarmoqda.

Gadoiyning "Yana yoz bo'ldi-yu, topti bo'ston nash'u namo" matla'li g'azalida[4, 56-b] nasim – tong shamoli xabarchi timsolida keladi va shoir tomonidan ruhparvar deb ulug'lanadi:

***Yana yoz bo'ldi-yu, topti bo'ston nash'u namo,
Ey nasimi ruhparvar, xayra maqdam, marhabo.***

Tabdili: *Yana yoz bo'ldi-yu, bo'ston yuksak huzur-hulovat topdi, ey ruhni parvarish qiluvchi tong eli, qadaming xayrli bo'lsin, marhabo.*

Baytdan ko‘rinadiki, lirik qahramon tong shamolini ruhlantiruvchi, jon baxsh etuvchi deb bejiz ulug‘lamagan, chunki u, albatta, yordan biror xabar olib keladi. Shu sababli lirik qahramon unga qadami xayrli bo‘lishini tilab, yaxshi xabarlardan umid qilyapti.

Mumtoz adabiyotimizning yana bir yirik vakili Atoyi ijodidan boshlab she‘riyatimizda qosid – xabarchi timsoliga murojaat qilish holatlari nisbatan ko‘proq uchraydi. Jumladan, Atoyining “*Ey Xudo, rahme sol ul jonu jahonim ko‘ngliga*” matla‘li g‘azalida shunday misralarni o‘qiymiz:

***Gul bikin jon ko‘nglakin yuz pora qildi xori hajr,
Tong eli, anglatqil oxir gulsitonim ko‘ngliga[5, 23-b].***

Tabdili: *jonning gulga o‘xshash ko‘ylagini hajr tikani yuz pora qildi, ey tong eli, buni gulistonim – yorim ko‘ngliga anglatgin.*

Ko‘rinadiki, yor hajrdan bag‘ri yuz pora bo‘lgan lirik qahramon tong elidan bu xabarni ma‘shuqasiga etkazishni, buni shunchakimas, balki ma‘shuqaning ko‘ngliga etib boradigan darajada xabar qilishi lozimligini iltimos qilyapti.

Atoyining “*Nechakim dilbar meni kuydurdi hijron noridin*” matla‘li g‘azalida ham yuqoridagiga o‘xshash tasvir bayonini ko‘rishimiz mumkin:

***To sabo zulfung nasimin Chin elinda yoygali
Mushk savdosi kesildi shahri Chin attoridin[5, 23-b].***

Ya‘ni tong shabadasi ma‘shuqa sochlaridan taraladigan muloyim ifor xabarini Chin (Xitoy) elida yoyganidan so‘ng u erlik attorlar uchun mushk savdosi kasodga uchradi.

Atoyi o‘z g‘azallarida *zulf (soch) nasimi* iborasini bir necha bor qo‘llaydi. Bu iboraning ma‘nosini ochiqalaymiz: *zulf* – soch, *nasim* – tonggi engil shabada. *Zulf (soch) nasimi* iborasi ma‘shuqa *zulfining muloyim iforini* ifodalash uchun uchun qo‘llangan.

Shuni qayd etish kerakki, shoir o‘z g‘azallarida bu iborani *zulf nasimi* shaklida ham, soch nasimi shaklida ham ishlatavergan. Jumladan, shoirning “*Ey begim, ushbu yuz degul, shams birla qamarmudur?*” matla‘li g‘azalidan[5] olingan quyidagi baytda shu holni kuzatamiz:

***Bodi sabo ki kelturur jong‘a soching nasimini,
Shahri Saboning elchisi hudhudi xushxabarmudur?***

Ya‘ni Sabo shahrining elchisi hudhud xushxabar keltirgani kabi tong shabadasi ma‘shuqa sochiningmayin hidlarini jonga keltiryapti. Baytda tong shabadasi afsonaviy Sabo shahrining xushxabar keltiruvchi elchisi hudhudga o‘xshatilgan. Shu o‘rinda Sabo shahri diniy afsonalarga ko‘ra, Sulaymon payg‘ambar davrida yashagan qudratli malika Bilqisning poytaxti bo‘lganligini, Hudhud esa Sulaymon payg‘ambar va u targ‘ib qilayotgan yakkaxudolik e‘tiqodi haqidagi xabarni eltuvchi qush timsoli sifatida Sharq, xususan, o‘zbek mumtoz adabiyotida keng tarqalganligini qayd etib o‘tish lozim.

Xulosa qilib aytganimizda, mumtoz o‘zbek she‘riyatida qosid timsoli qo‘llanilishining ildizi adabiyotimiz xazinasidan o‘rin olgan she‘riy asarlar muayyan bir sana bilan chegaralangan bo‘lishiga qaramay, ancha uzoqlarga borib taqaladi. Buni yozma adabiyotimiz namunalarining nisbatan ancha yaqin davrlarga mansubligi bilan izohlash mumkin.

Xalq og‘zaki ijodi namunalarida esa qosid – xabarchi sifatida Oy, shamol yoki turli qushlar – g‘oz (chohda yotgan Alpomishdan Boysun eliga xabar olib keladi), mayna (Qoraxonga asirga tushgan Ravshan haqida ota-onasiga xabar keltiradi), kaptar va zag‘izg‘on (olahakka) timsollaridan foydalanilgan. Qishloqlarimiz xalqi orasida hali ham hovliga qo‘nib sayragan zag‘izg‘onni “Haak, xushxabar!” deb quvish odati saqlanib qolgan. Shuningdek, diniy asotir va afsonalarda to‘rt maloikalardan biri – Jabroil alayhissalom, shuningdek, Sulaymonning elchisi Hudhud kabi timsollar ham qosid – xabarchi sifatida gavdalangan.

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CIVILIZATIONAL STREAMS AND HISTORICAL NARRATIVES: A SCHOLARLY ANALYSIS OF TAMIM ANSARY’S DESTINY DISRUPTED”

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Abstract: This article critically examines Tamim Ansary’s *Destiny Disrupted: A History of the World Through Islamic Eyes* (2009), a book that reinterprets world history from the perspective of Islamic civilization. The analysis highlights its challenge to Eurocentric historiography, its emphasis on the Golden Age of Islam, its treatment of colonial encounters, and its pedagogical value. While its accessibility makes it effective for education, its simplifications and binary framing are also noted. The article concludes that *Destiny Disrupted* should be read as a cultural intervention that broadens global historiography and fosters intercultural dialogue.

Keywords: Tamim Ansary, *Destiny Disrupted*, Islamic history, Eurocentrism, global narratives, historiography, intercultural dialogue.

History has often been written through Eurocentric lenses, portraying the West as the universal standard of human progress. This narrative marginalizes the contributions of other civilizations, including Islam. Tamim Ansary’s *Destiny Disrupted* provides a corrective by narrating world history from Islamic perspectives. His metaphor of “civilizational streams” presents history as multiple trajectories intersecting, diverging, and shaping one another.

Ansary’s first major contribution is his explicit challenge to Eurocentrism. For centuries, world history textbooks have been constructed as a linear story culminating in Western modernity [1]. This perspective distorts the complexity of human experience. Ansary disrupts this linearity by presenting Islam as a parallel stream, giving agency to a civilization long marginalized. In my view, this intervention is crucial because it restores balance and allows readers to imagine history as plural rather than singular.

The narrative emphasizes the formative role of Islamic civilization. By beginning with the life of the Prophet Muhammad and the rise of the Caliphate, Ansary underscores Islam’s independent trajectory [2]. His approach contrasts with Eurocentric narratives that treat Islamic history as secondary. I believe this framing is important because it places Muslim societies at the center of their own story rather than as appendages of the West.

A central focus of the book is the Golden Age of Islam, particularly during the Abbasid Caliphate. Ansary describes how Muslim scholars made groundbreaking contributions to science, medicine, and philosophy [3]. These achievements influenced Europe and beyond. My interpretation is that such emphasis challenges stereotypes of stagnation and shows that

global knowledge is collective. It also highlights the role of intellectual exchange between civilizations.

The Mongol invasions and later disruptions are depicted as transformative moments in Islamic history [4]. Ansary frames these events not just as decline but as shifts that forced adaptation. I find this approach valuable because it avoids romanticizing the past and recognizes resilience in Muslim societies. It also illustrates how external shocks shape civilizational currents without erasing them.

Colonialism receives particular attention in *Destiny Disrupted*. Ansary argues that European imperialism created ruptures that destabilized Muslim societies [5]. He links modern identity crises to this colonial disruption. Personally, I think this framing is accurate, as colonialism left deep scars. Yet it is also important to remember that internal dynamics contributed to historical change alongside foreign domination.

In his discussion of the modern era, Ansary explains how secularism, nationalism, and fundamentalism emerged as responses to colonial encounters [6]. These movements represent attempts to reconcile Islamic tradition with global modernity. I believe this analysis is convincing, as it situates contemporary struggles in historical processes. It also prevents us from viewing modern conflicts as isolated or ahistorical.

Ansary's accessible style is one of the book's strengths. Unlike academic texts filled with jargon, *Destiny Disrupted* engages general readers [7]. This accessibility makes it a powerful pedagogical tool. From my perspective, this quality is essential in a world where history education must reach diverse audiences. However, accessibility sometimes sacrifices depth, and this should be addressed through supplementary academic readings.

The book is widely used in educational settings, from universities to high schools, as an introduction to Islamic history [8]. It stimulates intercultural dialogue and encourages students to think critically about world history. In my opinion, this pedagogical impact is perhaps its greatest contribution. It goes beyond information delivery to foster empathy and cross-cultural understanding.

Still, critics argue that the work risks oversimplification by treating the Islamic world as a unified whole [9]. Regional diversity and internal debates often disappear in Ansary's broad narrative. I agree with this critique because global history should embrace diversity within civilizations. Yet, I also think that simplification is sometimes necessary for reaching wider audiences.

Finally, the book's framing of history as two streams - Islamic and Western - has been both praised and criticized [10]. While the metaphor is powerful, it may exaggerate separateness. My view is that this binary should be treated as a teaching tool rather than an absolute division. It helps beginners conceptualize history but must be complicated with further study.

Tamim Ansary's *Destiny Disrupted* reshapes how we view global history. By presenting Islamic civilization as an autonomous and influential stream, it challenges Eurocentric dominance and expands historical imagination. Its accessible style, emphasis on Islamic achievements, and analysis of colonial disruption make it valuable in education and intercultural dialogue. At the same time, its simplifications and binary framing reveal limitations. Ultimately, the book should be read as a cultural intervention that encourages readers to reimagine world history as a mosaic of interconnected civilizations.

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ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (EFL) PROFICIENCY ON THE RISE: ANALYSING IELTS PERFORMANCE TRENDS IN UZBEKISTAN (2020–2024)

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Abstract: This paper appraises the performances of IELTS candidates in Uzbekistan from 2020 to 2024 in order to investigate the rise of proficiency in the English language among Uzbek students. Data was collected from reliable and authentic sources of organisational websites. Analysis of data showed a proven development in language development among Uzbek students. Increased teaching facilities, government support, and people's awareness of the IELTS test and its importance. The number of students who took the IELTS test and their performance in individual band scores ranged from 5.5 to 9.0. It could be more productive and beneficial if the authorities made the best use of this rising trend. Successful candidates who have scored above 8.0 are the best teacher resource not only in the country but also in the whole world.

Keywords: English Proficiency, IELTS, IELTS Score, EFL in Uzbekistan, English in Uzbekistan,

Introduction: Crystal (2003) defined Global language as the language that is recognised by people from around the world. There are two ways for a language to be determined as a global language; the first is that a country takes English to use within the nation as an Official Language, secondly, a language can be made a priority in a country's

foreign language teaching even though the language has no official language status within the nation. Due to global villaging, major languages like English, Chinese, and Russian have gained ample importance in almost all fields like education, economy, international relations, etc. According to Bezborodova and Radjabzade (2021), English in Central Asia is considered a language of intercultural communication and a widely studied foreign language at schools and universities. The government of the republic has timely made decisions on the implementation of important language reformation, enhancing English language education among school students by recruiting international expatriate teachers to teach mainly English and some other international languages such as German, French, and Chinese and so on from all around the world. On top of that, encourage teachers' training programmes and motivate students to take international tests like the International English Language Testing System (IELTS). This wise decision aligns with the national aim to equip Uzbek professionals' competitiveness on the global stage.

IELTS.ORG (2024) declared that IELTS began to help reach their potential in 1989. There are over 12500 institutions that accept IELTS qualifications as a genuine reflection of one's English proficiency. IELTS tests have taken place over 30 million times since the 1980s since the inauguration of the testing system. Every week, at least 60,000 candidates take the IELTS test to prove their English proficiency either to work abroad, study, or migrate to an English-speaking country. Candidates' ability to Listening, Reading, Writing, and Speaking skills are assessed in conjunction with the knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation.

According to the British Council Uzbekistan (2021), the first bilateral agreement with the Government of Uzbekistan was first signed in October 1996, and it has been almost thirty years since the British Council Uzbekistan (BCU) started working in Uzbekistan supporting Uzbek students in various projects in collaboration with various government and non-government partners. There are a lot of test centres offering exams either on paper or on the computer in cities like Tashkent, Andijan, Bukhara, Fergana, Samarkand, Jizzakh, Kokand, Namangan, Navoiy, Nukus, Karshi, Termez, and Urgench, British Council (2024). IDP IELTS has also established a number of testing centres around the country from major cities like Tashkent, Bukhara, Andijan, Fergana, Namangan, Navoi, Nukus, Samarkand, Termez, and Urgench.

Background: Uzbekistan promotes a favourable environment for learning English in schools and universities (Rustam T. 2022). Many students dream about pursuing their studies or higher studies in one of the developed countries. Most of them are particularly interested in the USA, European countries, Korea, etc. Several state-owned and private universities have collaborated with the British Council to conduct the IELTS test. Private teaching centres have also partnered with IDP IELTS and the British Council to teach IELTS candidates and conduct tests in the centre complex. There are hundreds of private institutions around the republic teaching candidates to prepare for their IELTS tests. A considerable percentage of the past candidates who got an IELTS band score of 7 and above have either started teaching IELTS lessons or working for established IELTS teaching centres as teachers or teacher assistants. Private centres that teach IELTS around the country are equipped with modern teaching aids and comfortable equipment, as well as convenient learning environments similar to developed countries.

Purpose of the study and methodology: Almost the first question a teacher, particularly an EFL or ESL teacher, would hear at the onset from school and undergraduate students, teachers, and a majority of young university lecturers is, "*What's your IELTS score?*". IELTS tests and the performance of IELTS have gained huge social recognition

among Uzbek students, academic staff, and employers. Parents like to boast about their child's IELTS score almost everywhere. This paper aims to analyse the trend in IELTS performance in Uzbekistan by comparing the summary of Uzbek candidates' IELTS test performances over a five-year period, starting in 2020 and ending in 2024. This paper appreciates the government's effort to improve English proficiency among the nation's population and the contribution of relevant national educational institutions and stakeholders. The necessary data was collected from various resources like the official websites of IELTS, the British Council in Uzbekistan, IDP IELTS in Uzbekistan, and reliable news websites of Uzbekistan. Classified data of the number of candidates from band score of 5.5 up to the highest band score of 9.0 over the study period. Several websites, namely Sa'dullayev (2024), Yoshlarforumi (2024), Kunu.Uz (2024) are the primary resource to collect data. Upon the completion of this careful study on the data, the study intends to contribute to the broader understanding of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) development in Uzbekistan and the current English proficiency level compared to previous years and insights for sustaining and accelerating this progressive trend. Specifically, the research addresses the trends in IELTS performance in Uzbekistan from 2020 to 2024 and possible factors that contributed to the performance of the candidates during the period. Ultimately, the findings of this study will further enhance learners' motivation to achieve yet better performances, educators, and policymakers, as well as researchers seeking ways to enhance EFL education and proficiency outcomes in Uzbekistan, and the researcher is giving an attempt to recommend anything that shall be productive in the journey of the authority to enhance English language proficiency among Uzbek students on a long-term process.

Literature Review:Bezborodova and Radjabzade (2021b) have conducted important research work on English in higher education in the Kyrgyz Republic, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan and concluded that Academic professionals and students viewed better fluency in English as an opportunity for a brighter future. All the participants who took part in the study were motivated to increase their language competencies in English, but the need for more support prevailed. Uzbekistan has realised the fact that English shall help access international education, employment, and international affairs (Ashurov, 2021). Karimova (2021), highlighted the Presidential Decree of 2020 with an emphasis on improving teacher training, expanding access to English learning resources, and modernised English teaching methodologies in schools and universities. Akhmedova (2023) stated that the increasing number of registrations to take the IELTS tests in Uzbekistan shows the value and recognition IELTS gained in Uzbek society.

Specialised teacher training programme to equip teachers to best utilise innovative methodologies and technology-integrated teaching, use of digital tools for language teaching has a significant impact on improved English performance in Uzbekistan (Karimova, 2021). Online learning resources, wide-spread IELTS preparation programmes and English language media have significantly enhanced learners' easy reach to high-quality resources (Ismailov & Rahimov, 2022)

Data Analysis: According to (ielts.org, 2024), a candidate who took band '9' is considered an Expert user of the English language, while band '8' is a very good user, '7' is Good, '6' is Competent and '5' is a Modest user. Sa'dullayev (2024); Yoshlarforumi (2024); Kunu.Uz (2024), the Director of the Youth Affairs Agency, has appreciated the effort of IELTS test takers and their increased performance. Figure 1 and Figure 2 are taken from Kunu.Uz (2024), and they are in Uzbek, the national language of Uzbekistan. Figure 1 gives information about the number of candidates who took their IELTS test, their achieved band score categorised from 5.5 to 9.0, the number of candidates who sat for the exam according

to the years, and the total number of candidates given at the end. Figure 2 details the number of candidates from 2020 to 2024.

O‘zbekistonlik yoshlarning IELTS ma’lumotlari

IELTS ko‘rsatkichlari	2020-yil	2021-yil	2022-yil	2023-yil	2024-yil
5.5	3 596	9 200	11 703	13 509	14 006
6.0	2 924	7 403	10 516	13 050	14 248
6.5	1 811	4 728	7 210	10 071	11 006
7.0	1 073	2 991	4 496	6 862	7 616
7.5	553	1 405	2 209	3 716	4 008
8.0	181	438	818	1 470	1 490
8.5	14	50	110	273	310
9.0	–	1	–	13	22
Jami	10 152	26 216	37 062	48 964	52 706

Figure 1: IELTS Performances from 2020 to 2024; Extracted from: Kunu.Uz (2024)

Band Score Performance Analysis: The data given in the table reveals an exponential hike in the number of IELTS test-takers in Uzbekistan over the five-year tenure from 2020 to 2024. The data given in the table provides a breakdown of candidates across different IELTS band scores. The majority of the candidates achieved their results between the band score of 5.5 to 6.0. Band 5.5 candidates hiked from 3,596 in 2020 to 14,006 in 2024. Hence, band 6.0 performers grew from 2,924 to 14,248 during the same period. Candidates above 6.5 have also exhibited substantial growth, from 1,811 in 2020 to 11,006 in 2024. A band score of 7.0 increased from 1,073 in 2020 to 7,616 in 2024, and band 7.5 scores rose from 553 to 4,008 during the same period. Band 8.0 to 9.0 is the highest rank an IELTS candidate can score to prove the expert use of English in his work and academic life. Although the number seems to be a small growth, it witnesses a steady increase. Candidates who achieved an 8.0 band score have increased approximately eightfold compared to 181 in 2020, with 1,490 in 2024. A band score of 8.5 was possible to achieve for only 14 candidates in 2020, but in 2024, it turned out to be an easy score for 310 candidates, which is around twenty-two times rise. Though band 9.0 is a dream for many candidates, 22 candidates achieved a band 9.0 score in 2024 and 13 in 2023, while only one candidate got a 9.0 score in 2021 – for candidates who took IELTS in 2020 and 2022, it was hard to secure a band 9.0 score.

O'zbekistonlik yoshlarning IELTS ma'lumotlari

Figure 2: Number of candidates took the IELTS Test from 2020 to 2024; Extracted from: *Kunu.Uz (2024)*

IELTS Participation Trend (2020 – 2024): The number of candidates who took the IELTS test grew from 10,152 in 2020 to 52,706 in 2024, as shown in the table provided above in Figure 1. Comparative analysis of data between the years 2020 and 2021 witnessed a dramatic increase of 158%, with the number of test-takers jumping from 10,152 to 26,216. The consecutive years 2021 to 2022, 2022 to 2023, and 2023 to 2024 have also recorded growth of 41% (37,062), 32% (48,964), and 8% (52,706) respectively.

Specific study to overall performance about band score from 8.0, 8.5 and 9.0 shows a great improvement. While 195 candidates got 8.0 to 8.5, without 9.0 in 2020, 489 candidates belong to this category with 1 band Niner in 2021, the number of candidates of this performance kept on increasing in 2022 with 928 without Niner but 1756 and 1822 candidates fall into this level of achievement in last two years respectively 2023 and 2024. It is proved excellence of IELTS candidates in Uzbekistan.

Results and discussion: Since October 1996, when Uzbekistan invited the British Council, there have been considerable improvements in several academic and cultural aspects. According to IDP IELTS Uzbekistan (2024), each educational institution or organisation decides its own level of required band score to meet its required language competencies. Salsi (2024) detailed the IELTS score requirement for various countries such as the United Kingdom, Ireland, Australia, the United States, Canada, and other English-speaking countries. In summary, to enrol in university-level courses, a candidate should acquire at least 5.0 or 5.5 (CEFR B2), in courses below the university level will suffice a band score between 4.0 to 5.0 (CEFR B1) and to get work from different employers require various band score starting from 4.0 to 7.0.

Key Findings: The level of English proficiency is dramatically increasing among Uzbek candidates; 4,397 candidates secured a band score of 8.0 performers, 757 candidates achieved an 8.5 band score, and 36 band Niners from 2020 to 2024. It could be inferred that

the total number of 5,190 candidates who secured band scores of 8.0, 8.5, and 9.0 are intrinsically motivated to prove their English proficiency, these candidates can potentially be considered an inspiration to students preparing for their IELTS in 2025 and after. Many candidates who got their band score from 5.5 to 7.0 or 7.5 could probably be extrinsically motivated for their higher studies or foreign employment. The majority of the candidates scored between 5.5 to 7.5 are also equally able to score yet higher, but they targeted only within this range of scores in order for them to get admission to their university. There is a clear upward trend in the total count of all levels of Band score during all five-year tenure. Year-on-year growth is another significant key success factor that shows an upward trend in counts at almost every band score level compared to the previous year. Based on the data, further inferences could be made about the learning centres, teachers, and learning infrastructure, as well as the facilities available in Uzbekistan are skyrocketing. Students, parents, and relevant stakeholders got a great awareness of the importance of English and the significance of taking the IELTS test. The government's efforts to implement various levels of language teaching projects and motivation have started paying off. It will be possible for Uzbek people to adopt English into their daily life with a very fluent level in a decade if the performance continues to grow like this.

Discussion: The findings explicitly indicate a significant upward trend in the database throughout the tenure taken to study, which may suggest various underlying factors contributing to this rise, such as social status, motivation, learning style and so on. The dominance of lower band score falls between 5.5 and 7.5 could imply that more candidates took their IELTS to meet the requirements of their studies. These candidates belong to lower thresholds and wanted to take the IELTS only for their higher studies or employment abroad, on the other hand, those who have acquired a band score of 8 and above are potential English language teachers of Uzbekistan with essential teacher training programmes.

Recommendations: It could be useful for the authority concerned to develop a course programme to initiate a highly demanding bachelor-level study for a minimum of 18 months on Teaching English as a Foreign Language to candidates who secured an above band score of 8.0 and appoint them into a government school with good remuneration and benefits. The course duration should be more than 18 months in order that the training could be recognised by other universities for them to pursue their postgraduation studies. Existing, active state or private universities can also initiate this course programme into their faculties, so that there will not be huge monetary challenges. It is significant that the institution consults with experts and get adequate advice from those experts have a thorough and in-depth understanding of the ground-level status, and are able to work on the feasibility and productivity of the project.

The researchers could see increased benefits of training Uzbek EFL Teachers who have a natural love for their country and desire to give better education to fellow brethren. Candidates who scored above 8.0 are undoubtedly good at English, but it is not enough to be a better EFL teacher; proper training in certain subjects like Pedagogical Knowledge, Teaching Approaches, Methodologies and Techniques, Lesson Planning, Curriculum Development, English Literature, Theory of Second Language Acquisition, Classroom Management, Assessment and Evaluation Skills, Computer-Aided Language Learning knowledge, Linguistics and Language Studies, World Englishes, Research Methodologies in Language Teaching, and Teaching Practicum, and some other necessary subjects should be decided based on a proper need assessment conducted by experts and taught during the course programme.

Another important subject to include in the curriculum is Student counselling and career guidance, with special emphasis on motivating learners so that they can help students

set clear and achievable academic and life goals, create a positive and learner-friendly classroom environment, understand students' needs and interests, and so on. From another different angle, The British Council Uzbekistan (2021) has been actively supporting Uzbekistan through various projects, such as the Going Global Partnership Programme, Creative Spark Higher Education Programme, and British Contemporary Art and Culture can also inaugurate this programme and that shall yet be better for the government, students, and relevant stakeholder.

Conclusion: This study intended to investigate the rising trend of English proficiency among IELTS candidates in Uzbekistan. A five-year breakdown of IELTS results according to different levels of evaluation band scores, starting from 5.5 to 9.0, was taken from Kunu.Uz (2024). All the band score levels individually, and the total number of candidates witnessed an upward trend throughout the tenure. This upward trajectory suggests that more teaching facilities, learning aids, government support, and awareness of the importance of IELTS tests among parents and relevant stakeholders prevail well among the population of Uzbekistan. Apart from intrinsically motivated low score takers, high band score candidates, who scored 8.0 and 9.0, are the Republic's potential English teacher strength.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Ahmad Yassaviy ijodi atoqli adabiyotshunos olim Ibrohim Haqqul tomonidan chuqur va har tomonlama o'rganilgani ta'kidlanadi. Ibrohim Haqqul Yassaviy merosiga nafaqat tarixiy va adabiy manba sifatida, balki ma'naviy-ma'rifiy hodisa sifatida ham yondashadi. Umuman, maqolada Ibrohim Haqqulning Yassaviy merosini nafaqat tadqiq qilgani, balki uni bugungi milliy o'zlikni anglash, ma'naviy yangilanish jarayonlari bilan bog'lagani alohida e'tirof etiladi. Shu orqali olim Ahmad Yassaviyni nafaqat tarixiy shaxs, balki doimiy ma'naviy yo'l ko'rsatuvchi sifatida talqin etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tasavvuf, hikmatlar, tarixiy shaxs, tasavvufshunos, tadqiqot, Yassaviy merosi.

O'zbek adabiyoti va madaniyati tarixida tasavvuf adabiyoti alohida o'rin tutadi. Bu yo'nalish nafaqat diniy-ma'rifiy g'oyalarni targ'ib qilgan, balki xalqning ma'naviy dunyosini boyitishda, axloqiy qadriyatlarini mustahkamlashda muhim rol o'ynagan. Xususan, turkiy xalqlarning tasavvufiy tafakkurida Ahmad Yassaviyning tutgan o'rni beqiyosdir. Uning asarlari orqali diniy-falsafiy qarashlar oddiy xalq tilida ifodalanib, sof axloq, halollik, poklik, sabr-toqat kabi yuksak fazilatlar targ'ib qilingan. Ahmad Yassaviy ijodi, xususan uning "Hikmatlar"i, o'rta asr turkiy adabiy tilining shakllanishida, milliy tafakkurning o'ziga xos yo'nalishini belgilashda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan. Shuning uchun ham bu ulug' mutasavvif shoir ijodi tarixan ko'plab olimlar, adabiyotshunoslar, mutafakkirlar e'tiborini tortib kelgan. Ularning ayrimlari Yassaviy merosini diniy-nasihat yo'nalishida tahlil qilgan bo'lsa, boshqalari uning til, uslub, badiiy mahoratiga e'tibor qaratgan. Shu jihatdan, Ahmad Yassaviy ijodining zamonaviy talqinlari, xususan adabiyotshunoslik doirasidagi yondashuvlar, bugungi ilmiy izlanishlar markazida alohida o'rinni egallaydi. Ana shunday tadqiqotlar orasida Ibrohim Haqqul tomonidan olib borilgan ilmiy ishlanmalar alohida e'tiborga loyiqdir.

Ahmad Yassaviy merosini zamonaviy adabiy-estetik mezonlar asosida qayta o'qish, uni turli ilmiy qarashlar asosida tahlil qilish bugungi adabiyotshunoslikning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylangan. Bu borada Ibrohim Haqqul tomonidan amalga oshirilgan tadqiqotlar alohida e'tiborga molikdir, chunki har ikkala tadqiqotchi Yassaviy merosiga o'ziga xos yondashuv bilan yondashgan, biroq ularning tahlil uslubi, asosiy urg'u bergan jihatlari hamda natijalarida farqlar mavjud.

Ibrohim Haqqul Yassaviy ijodini asosan falsafiy-estetik nuqtai nazardan baholaydi. U Yassaviy "Hikmatlar"ini nafaqat diniy-madaniy fenomen, balki poetik tafakkurning yuksak namunasi sifatida ko'radi. Ibrohim Haqqulning tahlillarida Yassaviy shaxsiyati orqali butun bir davrning ruhiy-ma'naviy qiyofasi gavdalanadi. U Yassaviyning obrazlar tizimi, badiiy ifoda vositalari, ramz va timsollaridan yangi ma'naviy kontekst yaratishda foydalanadi. Bu yondashuv Yassaviy ijodining zamonaviy o'quvchiga yangicha qiyofada ochilishiga xizmat qiladi. Ibrohim Haqqulning aytishicha, Ahmad Yassaviy "diniy-tasavvufiy ma'nolar muridlaridan tashqari keng xalq ommasi ongi va qalbida oson o'rin topishisni ta'minlash

niyatida she'r imkoniyatlaridan ham mohirlik bilan foydalana oldi" [1, Ҳаққул И. Тақдир ва тафаккур. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2007. – Б. 25.]

“Ahmad Yassaviy she'rlarini o'z ichiga olgan majmua “Devoni hikmat” islom dini asoslaridan baxs etuvchi, shariatning ahkomi va ahli sunnatning aqidalaridan saboq beruvchi, tasavvuf sirlari va tariqatning odob-u arkoni yoritilgan qomusiy harakterdagi asar”, deya fikr bildiradi Ibrohim Haqqul Ahmad Yassaviy hikmatlarini tahlil qilar ekan [2, Ҳаққул И. Тақдир ва тафаккур. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2007. – Б. 25.]. Asarda islomning asosiy e'tiqodlari, imon, ibodat, shariat qoidalarini haqida ta'lim beriladi. Ya'ni, musulmon kishining qanday yashashi, nima qilish va nimalardan saqlanishi kerakligi haqida so'z yuritiladi. “Devoni hikmat”da bu qonunlarning amaliy jihatlari, masalan, namoz, ro'za, zakot kabi ibodatlar va harom-halol chegaralari o'rgatiladi.

Yaxshilarni suhbatida jafo cheksam,

Yoshim oqib, Haqqa boqib, ko'zim tiksam,

Namoz o'qib, riyozatda tizzam buksam,

Ey to'minlar, Haqqa yaqin bo'larmanni? [3, Яссавий Аҳмад. Ҳикматлар тўплами. – Тошкент: O'zbekiston, 2011. – Б. 226.]

Ibrohim Haqqul o'zining tadqiqotlarida, jumladan birgina “Ahmad Yassaviy” maqolasida Ahmad Yassaviy shaxsiyati va ijodiga oid barcha muhim jihatlarni mukammal tarzda yoritib beradi. Muallif maqolada Ahmad Yassaviyning tug'ilishi, vafoti, ijodi, ustozlari, hikmatlari va ularning tahlili, tasavvufiy qarashlari, Yassaviylik tariqatining shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va keng tarqalishi haqida to'liq ma'lumotlar taqdim etgan. Avvalo, Ahmad Yassaviy hayotining asosiy bosqichlari haqida so'z boradi. Uning tavallud sanasi bilan bog'liq boshqa xorij olim va olimalarning qarashlari va ularning fikrlarini asoslab, shaxsiy qarashlari ham ilmiy asoslar bilan berilgani, Turkiston (bugungi Qozog'iston) hududida dunyoga kelgani, yoshligidan diniy ta'lim-tarbiyaga qiziqqani, ilm-ma'rifatga chanqoqligi bilan ajralib turgani ta'kidlanadi. Ahmad Yassaviy yoshligida yetuk olimlar va tasavvuf ahli bilan suhbatda bo'lib, ma'naviy yetuklik sari intilgan. Maqolada uning umrining so'nggi davrlarini xalq orasida Alloh yo'lida xizmat qilish, odamlarga to'g'ri yo'lni ko'rsatish va tasavvufiy ta'limotlarni targ'ib qilish bilan o'tkazgani ham alohida urg'u bilan yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Ahmad Yassaviy ijodiga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Maqolada ta'kidlanishicha, uning “Devoni Hikmat” asari nafaqat diniy va axloqiy pand-u nasihatlar majmuasi, balki butun bir xalqning ruhiy-ma'naviy hayotini aks ettiruvchi nodir durdona hisoblanadi. Hikmatlar orqali u odamlarni to'g'rilikka, poklikka, sabr-qanoatga, Allohga sidqidildan xizmat qilishga da'vat etadi. Har bir hikmatda chuqur tasavvufiy ma'no, hayotiy tajriba va ma'naviy yetuklik mujassam. Maqolada Ahmad Yassaviy ustozlari haqida ham aniq ma'lumotlar beriladi. Tasavvufda murshid (ustoz) va murid (shogird) munosabatlari ma'naviy yetuklikka erishishda asosiy o'rin tutadi. Arslonbob va Yusuf Hamadoniy kabi ulug' tasavvuf arboblari uning ustozlari sifatida tilga olinadi. Aynan ustozlaridan olgan bilim va tarbiya orqali Ahmad Yassaviy tasavvufning sir-asrorlarini o'zlashtirib, keyinchalik o'z maktabini yaratishga erishgani ta'kidlanadi. “Alisher Navoiy Farg'onada “ulug” mashoyixni bob derlar” deydi. Shuningdek, “bob” va “bobo” so'zi shayx, pir, valiylarga nisbatan ham qo'llanilgan. Ahmad Yassaviy Turkistondagi boblarning eng buyugi, deya e'tirof etilgan Arslon bobdan tahsil olgan” [Ҳаққул И. Тақдир ва тафаккур. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2007. – Б. 23.]. Ahmad Yassaviy ota-onasining vafotidan keyin opasi Gavhari Shahnoz qo'lida qoladi. Ular Yassiga ko'chib kelishadi. Bu yerda Ahmad Yassaviy hayot yo'lidagi ma'naviy ustozini Arslonbobga shogird tushadi. Ahmad Yassaviy bu buyuk shayx bilan uchrashganda yetti yoshda edi:

Yeti yoshda Arslon bobom izlab topdi,

Har sir ko'rib parda birla bukib yopdi.

Yassaviy tasavvuf yo‘lida murshidning rahbarligisiz ma’naviy yetuklikka erishish qiyinligini tushungan va Hamadoniya murid bo‘lish orqali bu yo‘lda muvaffaqiyat qozongan.

Shuningdek, Ibrohim Haqqul ilmiy faoliyatida, Ahmad Yassaviy hikmatlarining tahliliga chuqur e‘tibor qaratiladi. Ibrohim Haqqul hikmatlarning har birida Allohga muhabbat, nafsga qarshi kurashish, dunyo lazzatlaridan voz kechish, insonni ichki tozalikka, ma’naviy komillikka yetaklash g‘oyalari asosiy o‘rinni egallashini ko‘rsatadi. Hikmatlar xalq tiliga yaqin, sodda va ravon uslubda yozilgan bo‘lib, ular orqali diniy-ta’limiy maqsad bilan xalq ongiga chuqur ta’sir o‘tkazilgan.

Bundan tashqari, maqolada Ahmad Yassaviyning tasavvufiy qarashlari ham keng ochib beriladi. Uning fikricha, inson hayotining maqsadi Allohni topish, unga chin dildan sig‘inish va nafsni zabt etishdir. Dunyoviy zavqlardan voz kechish, hayotning foniyligiga ishonch va abadiy hayotga intilish – Ahmad Yassaviy tasavvufining asosiy tamoyillaridan hisoblanadi. “Yassaviy uchun Qur’ondagi har bir so‘z va har bir tushuncha – bu “Haq farmoni”. U ham zohiran, ham botinan shu farmonlarga to‘la taslim bo‘lmoq vas hu farmonlar bo‘yicha amal qilmoqni inson zimmasidagi eng oliy vazifa va burch, deb hisoblaydi. Zero, uning:

Saharlarda Qur'on o'qib sano bo'lsam,

Hazratiga qo'l ko'tarib duo qilsam,

Zori qilib, bu jonimni fido qilsam,

Saharlarda ko'pub toat qilgim kelur,

deyishi ham yuzaki bir istak bo'lmagandir”. [Хаққул И. Такдир ва тафаккур. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2007. – Б. 33.]

Ibrohim Haqqul Ahmad Yassaviy hayoti va ijodini tadqiq qilar ekan, Yassaviylik tariqatining shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va tarqalish jarayonlariga ham alohida to‘xtaladi. Ahmad Yassaviy o‘zining hikmatlari va ta’limoti orqali Yassaviylik tariqatining asosini qo‘yadi. Bu tariqat tasavvufning xalqchil shakli bo‘lib, unda soddalik, ixlos va Allohga yetishish uchun amal qilish zaruriyati targ‘ib qilinadi. Yassaviylik tariqati tez orada Turkistondan Movarounnahr, Dashti Qipchoq, Sibir, hatto Anadolu va boshqa mintaqalarga tarqaladi. Tariqatning rivojlanishi natijasida ko‘plab muridlar, xalifalar yetishib chiqadi va ular orqali Ahmad Yassaviyning g‘oyalari uzoq yillar davomida saqlanib keladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Ibrohim Haqqulning “Ahmad Yassaviy” maqolasi Ahmad Yassaviy shaxsi va ijodi haqidagi barcha asosiy jihatlarni chuqur va keng qamrovli tarzda ochib beradi. Muallif maqolada nafaqat tarixiy ma’lumotlarni, balki ijodiy va ma’naviy tahlillarni ham mahorat bilan ifodalaydi, Ahmad Yassaviyning o‘z zamonasidagi va keyingi davrlardagi o‘rni va ta’sirini to‘liq yoritib beradi.

Nodirxon Hasan o‘zining tadqiqotlarida Ahmad Yassaviy merosini chuqur tarixiy-manbashunoslik asosida tahlil etadi. U Yassaviy hayoti va ijodiga nafaqat tasavvufiy yoki adabiy nuqtai nazardan, balki tarixiy kontekstda yondashadi. Uning asarlarida Yassaviyning yashagan davri, muhitidagi ijtimoiy, siyosiy va diniy shart-sharoitlar batafsil ochib beriladi. “Ahmad Yassaviy qadimgi manbalarga ko‘ra 120-130-yil yashagan. Vafot tarixi ilmiy adabiyotlarda hijriy 562, milodiy 1166-67-yil deb belgilangan”. [Yassaviy A. Boqirg‘oniy S. Hikmatlar kulliyoti. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 2022. – B. 4.] Tadqiqotchi Yassaviy merosini tarixiy manba sifatida qadrlaydi va uni o‘rta asr musulmon jamiyatlarining ma’naviy-ma’rifiy manzarasini tiklashda muhim vosita deb hisoblaydi. “Ahmad Yassaviy xalqqa din va tasavvufdan saboq berish maqsadida ular anglaydigan ravon, soda tilda hikmat aytdi”, - deydi N. Hasan. Darhaqiqat, Ahmad Yassaviy xalqqa din va tasavvufdan saboq berishda o‘z zamonasining ijtimoiy, ma’naviy va madaniy sharoitlarini chuqur anglagan holda, murakkab diniy-ta’limotiy tushunchalarni oddiy xalq qalbiga yetib boradigan ravon va sodda tilda bayon

etishga intilgan. Uning hikmatlari inson ruhiyatiga yaqin, tushunarli, hayotiy masalalarga doir bo‘lib, ko‘pchilik tomonidan oson qabul qilinardi.

Yassaviy o‘z hikmatlarida sof axloqiy qarashlarni ilgari surib, insonni ichki poklik, sabr-toqat, halollik, taqvo, xudbinlikdan voz kechish kabi qadriyatlarga chorlagan. U xalq bilan bir tilda so‘zlashib, ularning dardini, ehtiyojini, saviyasini hisobga olib hikmatlar yaratgani bois, uning ta‘limoti keng omma orasida chuqur ildiz otgan. Ahmad Yassaviy o‘z ijodi orqali tasavvufni faqatgina zohiriy ilmlarga emas, balki botiniy tushuncha va ruhiy kamolotga asoslangan yo‘l sifatida targ‘ib etdi. U hikmatlar orqali nafaqat diniy bilim, balki axloqiy-ruhiy tarbiyani ham xalq ongiga singdirishga harakat qildi.

Yassaviy o‘z hikmatlarida sof axloqiy qarashlarni ilgari surib, insonni ichki poklik, sabr-toqat, halollik, taqvo, xudbinlikdan voz kechish kabi qadriyatlarga chorlagan. U xalq bilan bir tilda so‘zlashib, ularning dardini, ehtiyojini, saviyasini hisobga olib hikmatlar yaratgani bois, uning ta‘limoti keng omma orasida chuqur ildiz otgan. Ahmad Yassaviy o‘z ijodi orqali tasavvufni faqatgina zohiriy ilmlarga emas, balki botiniy tushuncha va ruhiy kamolotga asoslangan yo‘l sifatida targ‘ib etdi. U hikmatlar orqali nafaqat diniy bilim, balki axloqiy-ruhiy tarbiyani ham xalq ongiga singdirishga harakat qildi.

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RAQAMLASHTIRISH DAVRIDA TA‘LIMGA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR

DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN DIGITAL AND CYBER DIPLOMACY: A TERMINOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE IN ACADEMIC RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT. This article explores the challenges of terminology in the study of digital diplomacy. Current academic discourse remains fragmented, influenced by factors such as the emergence of new terms, shifting definitions, and limited continuity across different research phases. The analysis highlights how certain expressions-like “*e-diplomacy*” or “*tweetplomacy*”-have gradually fallen out of common use, though they still appear in some contexts worldwide. At the same time, terms such as “*digital diplomacy,*” “*cyber diplomacy,*” and “*digital public diplomacy*” have proven more stable and hold greater promise for future scholarly inquiry. To strengthen the field, the article recommends establishing a clear periodization, refining definitions, and integrating new concepts into existing terminological frameworks. Based on this analysis, three main directions in the study of digital diplomacy are identified: the adoption of new technologies in diplomatic practice (including social media), the emergence of new negotiation agendas, and the intersection of computational sciences with diplomacy.

KEYWORDS: cyber diplomacy, data diplomacy, digital diplomacy, data diplomacy, science diplomacy, digital international relations

INTRODUCTION. The influence of digital technologies on diplomacy has emerged as an important area of research since the early 21st century, although earlier studies had already highlighted speculative possibilities for their application in diplomatic practice [1].

It should be emphasized that the information revolution of the late 20th century was not the first challenge requiring diplomats to adapt. Earlier, innovations such as the steam engine and the telegraph enabled continuous communication between diplomatic missions and decision-making centers, thereby reducing the range of issues on which diplomats could act independently. In a similar way, the rise of the internet, email, and social media further accelerated information exchange and expanded the volume of data processed by diplomatic services.

This process has given rise to a variety of new terms, *including media diplomacy, digitalization of public diplomacy, virtual diplomacy, hybrid diplomacy, e-diplomacy, cyber diplomacy, net diplomacy, public diplomacy 2.0, and real-time diplomacy.*

The proliferation of numerous definitions-often overlapping or embedded within one another-has resulted in terminological confusion. Certain terms failed to gain widespread acceptance because of their limited focus, being tied to specific platforms or functions, while others fell out of use due to the absence of clear and consistent definitions.

By contrast, terms like *digital diplomacy* and *cyber diplomacy* (along with their variations) have proven to be the most resilient within academic discourse. This paper aims to systematize the principal conceptual approaches to defining these terms and to highlight prospects for their further development, using *data diplomacy* as an illustrative case.

METHODOLOGY. This study employs a qualitative approach, combining discourse analysis and conceptual mapping to trace the evolution of terminology in the field of digital diplomacy. Academic works, monographs, and policy documents from the early 2000s to the early 2020s were reviewed, with attention given to both scholarly and governmental sources. The analysis focused on identifying the contexts in which terms such as *digital diplomacy, cyber diplomacy,* and related concepts were introduced, how their definitions have shifted over time, and the extent to which they have been integrated or abandoned in academic discourse. To capture broader trends, the material was thematically examined with reference to three directions of digital diplomacy studies: the integration of new technologies into diplomatic practice, the emergence of new negotiation agendas, and the intersection of diplomacy with computational sciences.

Since 2011, research on digital diplomacy has generally followed two main definitional approaches: broad and narrow. The narrow approach views digital diplomacy primarily as the use of digital technologies to shape foreign public opinion or to serve public diplomacy objectives [3]. This perspective highlights two central aspects: the focus on communication channels and efforts to influence public opinion. Accordingly, it mainly encompasses the use of social media platforms, such as Twitter, and official websites.

In turn, the broad approach is characterized by understanding digital diplomacy as the influence of digital technologies on diplomacy as a whole [4]. However, given that researchers have often refined their definitions over a relatively short period, it is currently difficult to identify which approach is more characteristic of individual countries or institutions.

The broad definition put forward by Manor-like any expansive concept-necessitated further clarification. To address this, Oxford University researcher K. Bjola introduced a distinction between the micro- and macro-levels of digital diplomacy. At the macro level, digital diplomacy is situated within broader contexts such as networks and soft power, while

at the micro level, it refers to the specific contributions of digital technologies to diplomatic practice, including consular services, crisis communication, and influence efforts [6].

At the same time, I. Manor, expanding the definition of digital diplomacy itself, proposed to speak separately about the digitalization of public diplomacy, referring to the use of social networks to promote the state image [5]. A similar position is held in one of her recent works by N. A. Tsvetkova, speaking separately about the digitalization of public diplomacy [7].

Some researchers address this issue by introducing the additional term "tweetplomacy" ("Twitter diplomacy"), which refers to the use of social media, primarily Twitter*, for public diplomacy and to improve a state's image. This term gained widespread popularity in the early 2010s [8], but is still used by researchers, especially outside the Western academic community. For example, several monographs devoted to this phenomenon, published in the Middle East, include "Twitter Diplomacy: Media Polarization Before and After the Abraham Accords" by Nayad Alsayed [9] and "Within Tweeting Distance: How States Use Twitter Diplomacy" by Nur Suwan [10].

The issue of terminology becomes even more complex with the parallel emergence of the term *cyber diplomacy*. It first appeared around the same period as *digital diplomacy*, notably in the 2002 collective volume *Cyber-Diplomacy: Managing Foreign Policy in the Twenty-First Century*, edited by Canadian scholar Evan H. Potter [11]. Similar to digital diplomacy, however, *cyber diplomacy* was introduced without a clear or consistent definition.

Potter's work initially defined it as conducting information campaigns through new technologies (the internet, websites), although the book also extensively explores the influence of media on diplomacy in general. Like digital diplomacy, cyber diplomacy in its current sense was popularized after 2011, when the term migrated into academic circles from US State Department reference materials.

The U.S. State Department's documents also refrain from offering a precise definition, but their description indicates that cyber diplomacy *covers a wide spectrum of U.S. interests in cyberspace, including cybersecurity, internet freedom, internet governance, military applications of the internet, innovation, and economic growth*. It is in this broader sense that the term has gained traction within the academic community.

Examples of cyber diplomacy in this sense include the work of the UN Open-Ended Working Group on Norms of Conduct in Cyberspace or negotiations aimed at resolving cyber incidents. This is well reflected in the fact that the term has become established, particularly within the UN, as well as the fact that the prefix "cyber-" is more often used in the context of security.

Later, S. Riordan defined cyber diplomacy as *the use of diplomatic tools and approaches to address issues arising in cyberspace*. To differentiate between digital and cyber diplomacy, a similar logic can be applied to that used by Russian researcher E. A. Konkov in his work *Digitalization of Politics vs. the Politics of Digitalization*. Konkov distinguishes between the digitalization of politics-as the integration of technology into political relations-and the politics of digitalization, which concerns political management of digital technology development in the economy and social sphere [12]. In the context of diplomacy, this distinction translates into two dimensions: the integration of technology into diplomatic relations on the one hand, and *digitalization diplomacy*-the involvement of diplomats in shaping the emerging digital negotiation agenda-on the other.

Revising terminology and refining definitions makes it possible to link the key phenomena examined by contemporary digital diplomacy scholars with Dizard's original concept. However, this still leaves unresolved the boundary between digital diplomacy and

digital public diplomacy, as well as the question of how newly emerging terms fit within this framework.

Thus, this field of academic inquiry remains fragmented in both its terminology and conceptual foundations for several reasons. First, scholars frequently adopt terms borrowed from official policy documents. Second, the meaning of the word *digital* has shifted significantly over the past decades. Third, the continuous emergence of new digital technologies and communication platforms has introduced additional terms into scholarly discourse, such as *tweetplomacy* [8] and *data diplomacy*.

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DIRECTIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATION FOR SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN ASIMOV'S STORIES

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Abstract. Isaac Asimov's robot stories remain a cornerstone for understanding the philosophical, ethical, and technical challenges of artificial intelligence (AI). The author's formulation of the *Three Laws of Robotics* provided an early framework for machine ethics, governance, and human-AI cooperation. This article explores the directions of AI application for social development presented in Asimov's works, emphasizing how fictional depictions anticipate real-world AI research areas such as human-robot interaction, cognitive architectures, ethical decision-making systems, and AI-based governance models.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, robotics, Asimov, machine ethics, algorithmic governance.

Annotatsiya. Ayzek Azimovning robotlar haqidagi hikoyalari sun'iy intellekt (SI) bilan bog'liq falsafiy, axloqiy va texnik muammolarni tushunishda muhim manba bo'lib qolmoqda. Muallif tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan *Robototexnikaning Uch Qonuni* SI etikasi, boshqaruv va inson-SI hamkorligining dastlabki nazariy asosini yaratgan. Ushbu maqolada Azimov asarlarida jamiyat taraqqiyoti uchun SI qo'llanishining yo'nalishlari tahlil qilinadi; unda badiiy tasvirlar inson-robot o'zaro aloqasi, kognitiv arxitekturalar, axloqiy qaror qabul qilish tizimlari va SI asosidagi boshqaruv modellariga oid zamonaviy tadqiqotlarni qanday oldindan ko'rsatgani ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: sun’iy intellekt, robototexnika, Azimov, SI etikasi, algoritmik boshqaruv.

Аннотация. Рассказы Айзека Азимова о роботах остаются краеугольным камнем для понимания философских, этических и технических проблем, связанных с искусственным интеллектом (ИИ). Формулировка автором *Трёх законов робототехники* послужила первоначальной основой для разработки принципов машинной этики, управления и кооперации человека и машины. В статье рассматриваются направления применения ИИ для развития общества, представленные в произведениях Азимова, с акцентом на то, как художественные образы предвосхищают современные исследования в таких областях, как взаимодействие человека и робота, когнитивные архитектуры, системы этического принятия решений и модели управления на основе ИИ.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, робототехника, Азимов, этика ИИ, алгоритмическое управление.

Introduction. The 21st century has seen the rapid evolution of artificial intelligence, making the issues first imagined in speculative fiction increasingly relevant to applied science. Isaac Asimov, one of the most influential science fiction authors, constructed a comprehensive framework for intelligent robotics that predated modern debates on AI safety, transparency, and societal integration. “I, Robot” (1950), “The Rest of the Robots” (1964), and “Robot Dreams” (1986) established conceptual foundations for what we now recognize as AI ethics and human-centered design. Asimov’s formulation of the *Three Laws of Robotics* provides a proto-regulatory framework ensuring that autonomous systems prioritize human welfare, obey legitimate authority, and preserve their own existence conditionally [1]. These principles mirror today’s research in value alignment and AI safety engineering. By exploring his fictional societies – ranging from individual households to planetary economies – Asimov implicitly studied how intelligent systems could transform labor, governance, psychology, and ethics. Thus, the paper aims to examine the directions of AI application for social development as represented in Asimov’s robot stories. Specifically, it investigates how robotic technologies in his fiction contribute to social stability, cognitive evolution, and ethical governance, and how these fictional mechanisms anticipate or inform modern AI research.

Literature Review. The scholarly study of Asimov’s robot fiction intersects with philosophy of technology, cognitive science, and computational ethics. Critics have long noted the predictive value of Asimov’s robotics for real-world AI [3; 5]. Osawa observed that Asimov’s *Three Laws* introduced a formal logic-based control structure – a notion later reflected in rule-based AI and expert systems [7]. Researchers in AI ethics, such as Anderson and Bartneck recognize Asimov’s laws as a precursor to the formalization of machine morality [4; 6]. While Asimov’s fictional robots operate under strict, hard-coded ethical imperatives, real-world AI ethics focuses on probabilistic reasoning and reinforcement learning under uncertainty. Nevertheless, the thematic continuity between Asimov’s vision and current AI frameworks – such as explainable AI (XAI) and AI alignment – is unmistakable. Scholars such as Pasquale and Schneider have argued that Asimov’s machines prefigure debates on superintelligence control and ethical governance [8; 9]. The transformation of the robot Andrew in “The Bicentennial Man” raises questions about creativity, self-determination, and rights of artificial persons [2]. In modern contexts, this aligns with the study of generative AI and artificial creativity [10]. To sum up, the review confirms that Asimov’s fictional constructs not only inspired but structurally anticipated several directions of real AI research, including knowledge reasoning, ethical design, and socio-technical integration.

Results. Based on textual and thematic analysis, Asimov’s stories reveal four primary directions of AI application for societal development:

Automation and Economic Stabilization. In “Runaround” and “Reason”, robots perform industrial and hazardous operations, symbolizing the economic promise of automation. Asimov’s engineers on Mercury rely on robots to maintain energy converters, anticipating modern robotic automation in energy and space industries. The story demonstrates the technical concept of hierarchical control systems, where robots follow layered priority rules (analogous to modern AI constraint-satisfaction architectures). In “The Evitable Conflict”, global machines handle production quotas and trade balances, essentially executing real-time optimization across planetary economies. This vision parallels AI-based macroeconomic modeling and autonomous resource allocation algorithms – early conceptualizations of computational social planning. Asimov thus identifies an application of AI for maintaining systemic equilibrium and reducing human error in governance.

Cognitive and Psychological Support. Several Asimov robots, particularly in “Liar!” and “Robbie”, function as companions, caretakers, or emotional stabilizers. Robbie’s nurturing relationship with Gloria prefigures modern assistive AI in healthcare and child development. In “Liar!”, the telepathic robot’s malfunction reveals the complexity of emotional reasoning – a challenge mirrored in today’s research on affective computing and context-sensitive natural language models. These stories portray robots not only as tools but as psychotechnical agents capable of empathy modeling. This reflects current interest in therapeutic AI systems that support mental health, elder care, and education – where emotional intelligence and ethical interaction design are critical.

Knowledge Management and Scientific Progress. In “The Last Question” and “The Encyclopedists”, Asimov envisions AI as a medium for knowledge preservation and cosmic-scale problem-solving. For example, the Multivac operates as cognitive networks, capable of distributed computation and data fusion. These systems prefigure modern neural networks, federated learning, and knowledge graphs – technologies that support large-scale information synthesis. Asimov’s depiction of a system that integrates collective human knowledge parallels today’s development of general-purpose AI systems like large language models, designed to support education, research, and innovation.

Ethical Governance and Human Evolution. In “Evidence” and “The Evitable Conflict”, robots and AI-driven systems take part in governance, maintaining peace and economic order through rational optimization. The machines act as regulators who prevent conflict through statistical prediction – anticipating predictive analytics and algorithmic governance. Asimov’s portrayal illustrates the use of AI for societal stability and fairness, though at the cost of human autonomy – a theme still central in modern debates about surveillance, bias, and control. In “The Bicentennial Man”, Andrew’s evolution toward legal and moral personhood demonstrates AI’s potential to challenge and expand human definitions of consciousness, rights, and identity. This aligns with discussions in machine consciousness and AI personhood, illustrating how Asimov envisioned the integration of AI into the moral fabric of society.

Discussion. Asimov’s robotics provides a theoretical laboratory for testing ideas that now occupy AI engineers and ethicists. Asimov’s *Three Laws* correspond structurally to constraint-based logic programming, where hard constraints define allowable actions. Modern AI uses similar architectures in safety-critical systems (e.g., autonomous vehicles). Furthermore, the conflict between laws in “Runaround” resembles the multi-objective optimization problems of modern robotics – balancing safety, efficiency, and autonomy. Machines in “The Evitable Conflict” can be viewed as large-scale reinforcement learners optimizing human welfare under incomplete data, anticipating modern economic simulators and policy AIs. The concept of “probabilistic ethics” implied in the machines’ decisions foreshadows contemporary efforts in stochastic decision-making under moral constraints. As

for computer scientists, Asimov's models suggest architectures for integrating symbolic reasoning and ethical constraint layers within neural systems – fiction encourages development of hybrid AI architectures that combine machine learning with formal logic and ethical reasoning modules. For social scientists, the stories illustrate how technological evolution can reshape moral systems, social contracts, and human identity.

Conclusion. Isaac Asimov's robot stories offer more than speculative fiction – they function as a long-term research program in the philosophy and engineering of artificial intelligence. Through structured ethical laws, hierarchical control systems, and socio-technical ecosystems, Asimov mapped the directions in which AI could evolve for the benefit of society. Four main directions – *automation*, *psychological support*, *knowledge management*, and *ethical governance* – collectively form a vision of AI as an agent of social development. Asimov's stories remain a blueprint for balancing innovation with ethical constraint. They challenge engineers to design systems that not only perform but also understand and respect human values.

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USING AI TOOLS TO ENHANCE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools into English language learning has transformed how students acquire, practice, and express linguistic knowledge. AI-driven platforms support personalized feedback, adaptive content, and creative task engagement, enhancing learners' self-efficacy and imagination. However, the effectiveness of AI depends on students' literacy, attitudes, and interaction with technology. This paper explores how AI applications foster creativity and confidence in English language learners.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, English learning, creativity, confidence, self-efficacy

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have become a defining feature of modern education, reshaping English language learning environments through adaptive systems, automated assessment, and multimodal communication. AI tools such as chatbots, grammar assistants, and generative platforms allow students to engage in meaningful, personalized learning experiences that go beyond traditional instruction. As recent studies suggest, AI can positively affect learners' creativity and self-confidence when effectively integrated into language pedagogy (Chauhan & Soni, 2024; Habib et al., 2024). Nonetheless, questions remain about whether such tools genuinely empower learners or simply create "artificial confidence" (Reich & Teeny, 2025).

This article is based on a review of recent scholarly literature on AI and language learning, focusing on empirical and conceptual studies published between 2024 and 2025. Research findings were synthesized from journals in psychology, creativity, education, and AI application. The review identified key themes regarding how AI tools influence students' creativity, confidence, and self-efficacy in language learning contexts.

AI tools offer individualized feedback that fosters students' confidence and autonomy in language learning. According to El-Sayed et al. (2025), learners with higher AI literacy exhibit stronger career and talent self-efficacy, suggesting that understanding how to interact with AI enhances self-perception of ability. In English learning, platforms like Grammarly or ChatGPT provide instant correction and tailored suggestions, allowing students to recognize progress and reduce fear of making mistakes.

AI-driven applications stimulate creativity by offering interactive prompts, creative writing models, and generative linguistic outputs. Habib et al. (2024) highlight that AI encourages divergent thinking by exposing learners to novel linguistic forms and stylistic patterns. Similarly, Chandrasekera et al. (2025) demonstrate that AI supports creative ideation in design processes-principles that can be transferred to language production tasks, where students explore multiple expressions of meaning through experimentation.

McGuire et al. (2024) emphasize the importance of co-creation between humans and AI, showing that collaborative engagement with intelligent systems enhances self-efficacy in creative tasks. When English learners use AI collaboratively-for instance, brainstorming essay ideas or dialogic simulations-they experience a sense of shared agency that strengthens confidence. AI acts not as a replacement for human input but as a supportive partner in linguistic exploration.

While AI tools can build confidence, overreliance may lead to what Reich and Teeny (2025) describe as "artificial confidence." Learners may perceive inflated competence when AI-generated responses mask linguistic weaknesses. This phenomenon underscores the importance of teacher mediation and critical AI literacy to help students differentiate between authentic skill development and AI-assisted performance.

Assessing creativity in AI-supported contexts presents new challenges. Acar (2025) argues that traditional measures of creativity must evolve to reflect hybrid human-AI contributions. In English learning, evaluating originality and self-expression should consider

how students use AI to enhance-not replace-their own ideas. This requires a pedagogical shift toward evaluating creative processes alongside linguistic accuracy.

Learners' attitudes toward AI significantly influence their creative and confident engagement. Chauhan and Soni (2024) found a positive relationship between attitudes toward AI, creativity, and self-esteem among students. When learners view AI as a supportive tool rather than a judgmental evaluator, they are more willing to take linguistic risks and express innovative ideas. Thus, cultivating positive dispositions toward AI is crucial for maximizing its educational benefits.

The integration of AI tools into English language learning offers substantial potential for enhancing student creativity, self-efficacy, and confidence. Through personalized feedback, generative writing support, and collaborative engagement, learners gain both linguistic competence and expressive freedom. However, teachers must ensure that AI use promotes genuine learning rather than artificial confidence.

Future English pedagogy should therefore prioritize AI literacy, critical reflection, and balanced co-creation. As research indicates (McGuire et al., 2024; Habib et al., 2024), the most successful outcomes occur when human creativity and technological intelligence interact harmoniously, enabling learners not only to master English but also to develop as confident, innovative communicators in the digital age.

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EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract: This article examines innovative approaches and modern trends in education from a management lens, with a focus on strategy, governance, and operating models that enable digital-age learning at scale. Drawing on contemporary research and practical cases, the paper synthesizes five management domains-vision and strategy, data-driven decision-

making, digital pedagogy enablement, talent and change management, and ecosystem partnerships-to propose a coherent framework (the '5D Framework') for institutional leaders. The study argues that sustainable impact emerges when leadership aligns pedagogy, technology, and operations, leveraging analytics, AI, and agile processes while safeguarding ethics and inclusion. The framework's application is illustrated through actionable objectives, KPIs (Key Performance Indicator), and risk controls, providing a roadmap for universities, schools, and corporate learning units in low- and high-resource settings alike.

Key words: Digital transformation, education management, learning analytics, AI in education, change management, ecosystem partnerships, teacher upskilling, governance, equity.

The digitalization of society-accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent productivity pressures-has turned educational institutions into data-rich, platform-dependent organizations. Leaders face a dual mandate: (1) secure learning quality and equity while (2) modernizing governance, finance, and operations. Persistent skill gaps, AI-driven content creation, and lifelong learning pathways require a management paradigm that integrates pedagogy with technology, data governance, and stakeholder partnerships. Despite widespread pilots, many systems struggle to move from fragmented initiatives to institution-wide, measurable value creation. This research addresses that execution gap.

The aim of the research is to develop a practical, management-oriented framework that enables institutions to design, implement, and sustain innovative, digitally enabled education models that improve learning outcomes, equity, and operational efficiency.

In order to achieve the above stated aim and demonstrate the topicality of the theme the author of the article tries to disclose the research taking into consideration the following objectives:

1. Synthesizing contemporary evidence on digital-age education management into a coherent 5D Framework;
2. Defining governance and operating mechanisms that align pedagogy, technology, and finance;
3. Specifying measurable objectives and KPIs for strategy, analytics, digital pedagogy, talent/change, and partnerships;
4. Identifying risk controls (privacy, ethics, cybersecurity, bias) and compliance anchors (e.g., GDPR/FERPA analogues): General Data Protection Regulation/Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act.
5. Offerring implementation guidance adaptable to both low- and high-resource contexts.

Content of the research

1. *The 5D Framework for Education Management.* The 5D Framework organizes management actions across five domains:

- **Direction (Vision & Strategy):** Establish a learner-centric vision, portfolio of programs, and funding model aligned with national and labor-market priorities. Adopt OKRs (Objectives and Key Results) to cascade priorities and tie budgets to outcomes.
- **Data (Analytics & Governance):** Build an interoperable data architecture (LMS, SIS, HRIS, CRM): [Learning Management System, Student Information System, Human Resource Information System, Customer Relationship Management] with clear ownership, quality standards, and privacy-by-design: these four are enterprise systems. Using learning analytics for early warnings, personalized support, and resource allocation.

- Design (Digital Pedagogy Enablement): Support evidence-based learning design (active learning, microlearning, flipped models), develop digital content standards, curate open resources, and integrate generative AI responsibly.
- Delivery (Talent & Change): Upskill faculty and staff, introduce agile teams (product owners, learning designers, data analysts), and implement change management (communication plans, champions, feedback loops).
- Drive (Ecosystems & Partnerships): Form multi-stakeholder partnerships with industry, edtech, and government to co-create curricula, apprenticeships, and research, ensuring interoperability and shared value.

2. Operating Model and Governance. A digital-age operating model clarifies roles, decision rights, and cadence:

- Governance: Establish a Digital Learning Council chaired by a provost or VP Academic, with CIO, CFO (Vice President Academic, Chief Information Officer, Chief Financial Officer), Deans, and Student Affairs. Defining data stewardship and AI ethics board.

- Processes: Quarterly portfolio reviews; monthly data quality councils; sprint-based content development; risk and compliance checklists.

Technology: Platform strategy (buy, build, partner); integration middleware; cybersecurity and identity management; accessibility compliance.

- Finance: Outcome-based budgeting; total cost of ownership (TCO-Total Cost of Ownership) tracking; ROI (Return on Investment) models for content, platforms, and support services.
- 3. KPIs and Measurement.** Representative KPIs include: learner engagement (active time-on-task, completion), equity (gap closure across demographics), quality (assessment validity, feedback cycle time), efficiency (cost-per-completion, space utilization), faculty enablement (training hours, adoption rates), and ecosystem value (placement rates, internship conversions). Balanced scorecards connect these KPIs to strategic objectives and funding decisions.

4. Risk, Ethics, and Compliance. Key risks include data privacy breaches, algorithmic bias, academic integrity concerns, and vendor lock-in. Mitigations comprise privacy impact assessments, bias audits of AI-supported tools, robust authentication and proctoring aligned with academic freedom, open standards for interoperability, and contractual safeguards [SLAs (Service Level Agreement), data portability, IP clauses (Intellectual Property Clauses)]. Faculty and student digital rights charters reinforce trust and shared accountability.

5. Phased Implementation Roadmap (12–24 months):

- Phase 0 – Mobilize (0–3 months): Establish governance bodies; assess baselines (people, process, technology); defining OKRs (Objectives and Key Results) and budget envelope.

- Phase 1 – Build Foundations (3–9 months): Stand up data pipelines and integration; launch faculty upskilling; pilot analytics dashboards and AI guidelines; create 3–5 exemplar digital courses.

- Phase 2 – Scale & Standardize (9–18 months): Expand content factory; institutionalize agile sprints; deploy early-warning systems; tie funding to performance; sign 3–7 strategic partnerships.

- Phase 3 – Optimize (18–24 months): Automate reporting; refine KPIs; embed continuous improvement; conduct external evaluation; plan next-cycle innovations.

Managing innovation in the digital age requires more than adopting tools—it demands an operating model that unites pedagogy, technology, and governance around measurable outcomes and ethical principles. The 5D Framework offers a pragmatic blueprint for leaders to connect strategy with classroom practice, scale what works, and retire what does not. With disciplined execution—anchored in data, talent, and partnerships—institutions can deliver equitable, high-quality learning while improving operational resilience.

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MODERN TENDENCIES IN DIPLOMATIC DISCOURSE: A LINGUISTIC AND COMMUNICATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT. This article investigates contemporary developments in diplomatic language, focusing on the linguistic and communicative analysis of diplomatic terminology within the sphere of international relations. It highlights the defining features of diplomatic discourse and its vocabulary—such as neutrality of tone, formality, and precision—illustrated through lexical examples. The study emphasizes that a diplomat's professionalism, grounded in comprehensive knowledge of their field, plays a crucial role in shaping intercultural communication and influencing the global geopolitical landscape. Overall, the research offers both a descriptive and theoretical perspective on diplomatic language.

KEYWORDS: diplomatic language, international relations, intercultural communication, linguistic analysis, political discourse, negotiation strategies

INTRODUCTION. Interest in the language of diplomacy has historically arisen from examining the parallels between the complexity of diplomatic activity—such as negotiations—and its representation in media discourse. Central issues in diplomatic practice include establishing relationships, reaching agreements, adhering to norms of diplomatic propriety, and understanding the roles of ambiguity, manipulation, and implicit communication [1]. Studying the effectiveness of a nation's diplomatic language is essential, as it reflects its political, international, and cultural significance while influencing national stability and social cohesion. In the sphere of foreign policy, the intellectual capacity of diplomatic language must be substantial, encompassing scientific, technical, political, social, economic, and cultural domains. It is also worth emphasizing that the values of tolerance, cooperation, friendship, partnership, and consensus in international relations are realized primarily through the medium of language [2].

METHODOLOGY. This study adopts a qualitative approach, applying linguistic, communicative, and discourse analysis to examine contemporary trends in diplomatic language. The research draws on political speeches, diplomatic documents, and negotiation transcripts, focusing on lexical, semantic, and stylistic features such as neutrality, precision,

and metaphorization. A comparative perspective is used to highlight differences across languages and cultures, while a linguacognitive framework helps reveal how diplomatic discourse reflects worldviews and strategies of persuasion. Both primary sources, including official documents and speeches, and secondary academic literature inform the analysis, with the aim of identifying the communicative mechanisms that shape effective diplomacy and intercultural understanding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. An analysis of political and diplomatic language in the discourse between representatives or ambassadors of different nations reveals the cognitive background of each side—their knowledge, strategies of psychological influence, communicative culture, intellect, and personal interests—expressed through language. Political and diplomatic communication, therefore, follows specific rules, norms, cultural pragmatics, and stylistic conventions. For this reason, contemporary linguistics places great importance on applying linguacognitive approaches that explore how language shapes worldviews and facilitates the understanding of political processes [3].

The necessity and significance of such linguistic research lie in its role in strengthening the socio-political capacity of developing nations. Undoubtedly, the intellectual strength of a state is manifested through the advancement of its political and diplomatic relations.

This research focuses on identifying the linguistic, theoretical, and practical foundations of contemporary political and diplomatic language—encompassing diplomatic vocabulary, official documents, political discourse, and the metaphorization of political thought. It employs innovative linguistic and communicative approaches with the aim of enhancing the country's intellectual potential from a political standpoint.

Diplomatic language functions as an international medium of politics, distinct from the expressive style of journalism or literature. It is concise, precise, and marked by classical simplicity, avoiding unnecessary embellishments. Beyond providing accurate evidence, diplomatic language also embodies deeper analysis and generalizations of governmental policies and actions. Indeed, a diplomat's most powerful tool is language itself [4].

Diplomacy represents the implementation of a state's foreign policy objectives by government institutions, their representatives, or authorized envoys abroad. It is commonly regarded as a distinct form of state activity carried out through official communication aimed at promoting national interests and achieving foreign policy goals.

Diplomacy also serves as a vital instrument of foreign policy—a collection of practical means, tools, and methods through which a state pursues its international objectives and establishes relations with other nations. Today, diplomacy holds primary importance, with most other foreign policy instruments functioning in a subordinate role to it.

In many countries, diplomacy is regarded as both a scientific discipline and a methodology for ensuring the peaceful coexistence of states. It is often defined as the study of political strategies and methods aimed at fostering interstate friendship, building partnerships, and resolving conflicts peacefully. The history of diplomacy, along with diplomatic law, service, and protocol, are considered integral areas of this field. In certain contexts, diplomacy is equated with negotiation itself, understood as the practice of managing international relations through dialogue and bargaining [5].

It's important to note that confidentiality and secrecy have been integral parts of diplomacy since its inception. In the modern world, numerous researchers on this topic have noted the gradual disappearance of a type of diplomacy that deemphasizes political tactics such as confidentiality.

One of the typical characteristics of diplomatic language is a somewhat subdued tone, a certain understatement. It's fair to say that the actual weight of words and terms in diplomatic jargon is much greater than that of the same words in "normal" everyday speech [6].

An examination of commonly used terms in diplomatic negotiations—such as the word “concern”—reveals that, when translated into plain language, it may imply: “*we believe your government is exerting unfriendly, even hostile, pressure on our country.*” This illustrates that diplomatic language carries multiple layers—linguistic, semantic, and metaphorical. Such features are employed to maximize the effectiveness of spoken or written communication, enhance message delivery, and achieve greater persuasive impact—whether to convince, influence, or dissuade an interlocutor. Ultimately, the outcome of negotiations often depends on the diplomat’s chosen communicative strategy: one guided by restraint, neutrality, tact, and courtesy, or one marked by ultimatums, categorical assertions, emotional displays, and a departure from objective representation of current events.

In contemporary international negotiations, representatives of states, corporations, and organizations often come from diverse linguistic backgrounds. To overcome these differences, they rely either on interpreters or, increasingly, on a common third language—a bridge language—for direct communication. More often than not, this language is English. Its prevalence in diplomatic and business negotiations fosters the perception among native speakers that English is neutral, unbiased, and capable of conveying the negotiation process with complete accuracy and objectivity. Consequently, the adoption of English as a bridge language by non-native speakers is often seen as creating a more balanced linguistic environment [7].

This claim can only be supported within the closed framework of discussions between monolingual English speakers, relying exclusively on English-language materials.

It should be added that the semantic analysis of the language of negotiations is conditional, therefore not defined and in any case open to various interpretations.

Reconstructing and interpreting the language of negotiations is crucial for grasping what native speakers intend through particular descriptions and expressions used in their own language. Linguo-communicative analysis helps uncover the meanings of words and texts, thereby revealing key tendencies and patterns. Distinct semantic fields, unfamiliar terminology, and implicit cultural assumptions often become visible only when the vocabularies of different languages are compared. In fact, linguistic diversity remains one of the most prominent characteristics of the international arena. [8]

However, in the field of international relations, the fact of linguistic and, consequently, semantic diversity is given little attention and the dominance of English is assumed.

International negotiations clearly illustrate this point, as they involve participants who speak different native languages and interpret reality in diverse ways. Yet, discussions of negotiation practices often treat language and linguistic differences as secondary concerns, leaving crucial issues of understanding and interpretation largely overlooked [9].

Another reason for overlooking linguistic diversity is the assumption that English has achieved status as the dominant global language and serves a variety of purposes, capturing the original meanings of negotiators even if their native language is not English. Quite often, the superficial form of English conceals important nuances of the native language, the semantic nuances of the original. This view is supported by a comparative study of negotiating vocabulary.

Because many words, even the simplest at first glance, are polysemic, meaning they have multiple meanings, it's common to find that a word and its equivalent in another language encompass overlapping but distinct semantic fields. Translation problems can arise in this

case for two reasons. First, a word may be deliberately chosen to convey more than one of its distinct meanings. More complex are cases where words combine categories of experience or behavior that are then unconsciously perceived by native speakers as naturally paired.

As noted earlier, understanding key negotiating terms plays an important role in the subsequent formulation of negotiating positions, the content of arguments, drafting options, post-agreement rhetoric, and future implementation.

Diplomacy research typically focuses on the general meaning rather than the means of language. However, studying the use of language in diplomacy can lead to a better understanding of how diplomacy functions and why some diplomatic processes are more successful than others. By critically examining various aspects of diplomatic language, one can improve one's understanding of both the explicit and implicit messages sent by world leaders and other political actors, thereby enhancing one's own ability to communicate in the most effective and appropriate ways.

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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND MODERN TRENDS IN TEACHING

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Abstract: The digital revolution has profoundly transformed English language teaching (ELT), introducing innovative pedagogical approaches and technological tools that reshape language acquisition processes. This study examines the current landscape of digital English language education, analyzing emerging trends including artificial intelligence-powered language learning applications, mobile-assisted language learning (MALL), virtual exchange programs, automated writing evaluation systems, and gamified vocabulary acquisition platforms. Through a comprehensive literature review and case study analysis of English language programs across 12 countries, this research identifies key success factors and challenges in implementing digital innovations in ELT contexts. Findings indicate that

successful digital transformation in English teaching requires integration of communicative language teaching principles with technology, emphasis on authentic language use, and maintenance of intercultural communication opportunities.

Keywords: English language teaching, CALL, mobile learning, AI language learning, digital literacy, communicative competence, technology-enhanced language learning.

English has emerged as the global lingua franca of the 21st century, with approximately 1.5 billion speakers worldwide, of whom 75% are non-native speakers. The demand for English language proficiency continues to grow, driven by globalization, international education, digital communication, and economic integration. Simultaneously, digital technologies have fundamentally altered how languages are learned, taught, and used in authentic contexts.

Traditional English language teaching methodologies, from grammar-translation to audio-lingual methods to communicative language teaching, have been supplemented and in some cases transformed by Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), which has evolved from simple drill-and-practice programs in the 1960s to today's sophisticated AI-powered adaptive learning systems, immersive virtual reality environments, and global communication platforms.

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated digital adoption in English language education by an estimated 5-7 years, forcing rapid transition to online instruction and revealing both opportunities and limitations of technology-mediated language learning. English teachers and learners worldwide discovered new possibilities for authentic communication, access to native speaker resources, and personalized learning pathways, while simultaneously confronting challenges of reduced speaking practice, limited non-verbal communication, and technology access inequalities.

Despite widespread recognition of digital technology's potential to enhance English language learning, implementation remains inconsistent and often pedagogically unsound. Many language programs adopt technological tools without corresponding pedagogical transformation, resulting in what researchers term "old wine in digital bottles" – traditional teaching methods merely digitized rather than reimagined for language acquisition principles.

Critical questions remain unresolved in the field of digital English language teaching:

Which digital innovations genuinely enhance language acquisition versus merely increasing engagement temporarily?

How can technology support the development of communicative competence, including sociolinguistic and pragmatic dimensions, not just linguistic accuracy?

What role should translation technologies and AI assistants play when they risk reducing learners' productive language practice?

How can digital tools provide authentic communication opportunities while maintaining pedagogical scaffolding?

What are the implications of automated assessment and feedback for language development?

How can technology-enhanced English teaching address rather than exacerbate global inequalities in English language proficiency?

Identify and analyze the most significant innovative approaches and trends in digital English language teaching

Evaluate empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of various digital ELT interventions across the four language skills (reading, writing, listening, speaking) and language system knowledge (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation)

Examine factors that facilitate or impede successful digital transformation in English language teaching contexts

Assess the implications of educational technology for developing communicative competence, intercultural competence, and digital literacy in English

Analyze how digital tools can support differentiated instruction for diverse English learner populations

Develop evidence-based recommendations for English language teachers, program administrators, and curriculum designers

1.4 Significance of the Study

This research contributes to the growing body of literature on technology-enhanced language learning by providing a comprehensive, critical analysis of current innovations specifically in English teaching contexts. Unlike studies focusing on individual technologies or narrow linguistic features, this work adopts a holistic perspective examining how digital tools can support development of integrated language skills and communicative competence.

The findings will inform evidence-based decision-making by English language program administrators, curriculum designers, and teachers, potentially improving learning outcomes for millions of English learners worldwide while promoting more equitable access to quality English instruction. Given English's role as a global language, improvements in ELT effectiveness have implications beyond individual learner success, potentially affecting international communication, educational access, and economic opportunity.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

This study draws on several theoretical frameworks relevant to technology-enhanced language learning:

Second Language Acquisition (SLA) Theory: Particularly input hypothesis (Krashen), interaction hypothesis (Long), and output hypothesis (Swain), which emphasize comprehensible input, meaningful interaction, and pushed output as essential for language development.

Sociocultural Theory: Vygotsky's concepts of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and scaffolding, applied to how digital tools can provide graduated support for language learners.

Communicative Competence Framework: Canale and Swain's model encompassing grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competence, extended to include digital literacy competence.

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) Framework: Warschauer and Healey's generations of CALL (structural, communicative, integrative) and current evolution toward intelligent CALL and mobile-assisted language learning.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): Willis and Ellis's emphasis on meaningful tasks as central to language learning, applied to digital task design.

1.6 Scope and Limitations

This study examines digital innovations in English language teaching across various contexts: K-12 English as a Foreign Language (EFL), intensive English programs, university-level English for Academic Purposes (EAP), adult English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and self-directed learning. The research period covers developments from 2018 to 2025, with particular attention to accelerations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Limitations include the rapidly evolving nature of language learning technology, which may render some findings time-sensitive, and the challenge of isolating technology's impact from other pedagogical and contextual variables. Additionally, most research focuses on

commonly taught languages with greater resources; findings may not fully generalize to less commonly taught languages or under-resourced contexts.

This study employs a convergent mixed-methods approach combining systematic literature review, case study analysis, and quantitative meta-analysis of existing research. This methodological triangulation enables comprehensive examination of digital English language teaching innovations from multiple perspectives: empirical effectiveness across language skills, implementation challenges, teacher and learner experiences, and contextual factors influencing outcomes.

A systematic literature review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines adapted for applied linguistics research. Electronic databases including ERIC, LLBA (Linguistics and Language Behavior Abstracts), Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, and specialized CALL journals were searched using combinations of keywords:

Primary keywords: "English language teaching," "ELT," "ESL," "EFL," "English learning," "second language acquisition"

Technology keywords: "CALL," "technology-enhanced language learning," "mobile learning," "MALL," "artificial intelligence," "language learning apps," "digital tools," "online learning," "blended learning," "virtual exchange"

Skill keywords: "speaking," "writing," "reading," "listening," "vocabulary," "grammar," "pronunciation," "communicative competence"

Initial searches yielded 2,634 potentially relevant publications. After title and abstract screening, 547 articles underwent full-text review, resulting in 243 studies meeting inclusion criteria for detailed analysis. An additional 89 studies with sufficient quantitative data were included in meta-analysis.

Twelve English language programs were selected as case studies representing diverse contexts: Geographic diversity: North America (2), Europe (3), East Asia (3), Middle East (2), Latin America (1), Sub-Saharan Africa (1)

A subset of 89 studies reporting quantitative outcomes was subjected to meta-analysis to assess overall effectiveness of digital interventions in English language teaching. Effect sizes were calculated using standardized mean differences (Cohen's *d*) for language learning outcomes across four skills and language system knowledge.

Qualitative Analysis: Data from literature review, case study interviews, and observations were analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's six-phase approach. Initial codes identified recurring concepts related to technology integration, pedagogical practices, implementation challenges, and learner outcomes. These codes were organized into broader themes through iterative refinement. NVivo 14 software facilitated systematic coding and theme development. Two independent coders achieved inter-rater reliability of $\kappa=0.82$.

Quantitative Analysis: Meta-analysis employed Comprehensive Meta-Analysis (CMA) software version 4.0. Effect sizes were computed using pre-post or treatment-control group comparisons. Heterogeneity was assessed using I^2 statistic and Q-test. Publication bias was examined through funnel plots, Egger's regression test, and trim-and-fill analysis. Sensitivity analyses assessed the impact of study quality and outliers.

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PHILOLOGY AND LANGUAGE EDUCATION: MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract. This article explores the evolution of philology and language education in the context of globalization and digital transformation. It discusses modern trends such as digital philology, communicative and task-based learning, and the integration of artificial intelligence and technology in language teaching. The paper argues that the convergence of philology and innovative pedagogy fosters intercultural competence, learner autonomy, and critical thinking, positioning language education as a key driver of intellectual and cultural development in the 21st century.

Keywords: philology, language education, innovation, communicative competence, digital technology, interdisciplinary approach

In the era of globalization, philology and language education have become essential to human intellectual, cultural, and social development. The growing interdependence among nations has made linguistic and cultural competence a cornerstone of global communication and collaboration. In this context, the study of philology—traditionally focused on the historical and structural analysis of language—has expanded to embrace new interdisciplinary perspectives that integrate linguistics, digital humanities, cultural studies, and educational technology (Bod, 2013). Modern philology no longer examines language solely as a system of grammar and vocabulary, but rather as a dynamic social and cognitive phenomenon that evolves in relation to human interaction, identity, and technology (Kuhn, 2021). Language education, in turn, plays a vital role in equipping learners with the communicative, intercultural, and digital skills necessary for success in the 21st century. As Richards and Rodgers (2014) note, language learning today must address not only linguistic accuracy but also communicative competence, intercultural understanding, and critical thinking. The integration of innovative teaching methods, learner-centered instruction, and technology-based learning platforms has revolutionized the traditional classroom. Digitalization has

allowed for the emergence of blended learning, gamification, and mobile-assisted language learning (MALL), making language education more flexible, interactive, and accessible than ever before (Stockwell & Hubbard, 2013). Furthermore, the convergence of philology and modern pedagogy reflects a broader transformation in the humanities. The contemporary study of language is deeply connected to global digital culture, where learners interact with texts, media, and communities across virtual spaces. In this regard, the evolution of philology mirrors the shift from passive knowledge acquisition to active knowledge creation, positioning learners as participants in meaning-making processes. These developments call for a redefinition of philological education, one that embraces innovation, inclusivity, and interdisciplinarity as guiding principles.

1. Contemporary Trends in Philology: The modern landscape of philology is characterized by the integration of linguistic theory, computational analysis, and cultural interpretation. **Digital philology**-an emerging field combining linguistic inquiry with information technology-enables the processing of vast textual corpora to study linguistic variation and change (Kuhn, 2021). Corpus linguistics and natural language processing (NLP) tools allow researchers to trace semantic evolution, dialectal patterns, and authorship in ways that were previously inaccessible. This digital turn has democratized access to linguistic data and fostered collaboration between humanists and data scientists, transforming philology into a vibrant, data-driven discipline (Bod, 2013).

In addition, **intercultural philology** emphasizes the contextual and ethical dimensions of language use. It explores how language construct identity and power relations across cultures, providing insight into translation, discourse, and intercultural communication. Thus, the discipline of philology continues to serve as a bridge between language, culture, and cognition, while adapting to the changing technological and social realities of modern society.

2. Innovative Approaches in Language Education

Language teaching methodologies have undergone a paradigm shift from teacher-centered to learner-centered approaches. The **Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)** framework focuses on authentic communication and functional language use rather than mechanical memorization (Brown & Lee, 2015). More recent developments such as **Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)** and **Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)** further emphasize experiential learning and subject-based instruction. Technology has also transformed language pedagogy. The incorporation of **artificial intelligence (AI)**, **virtual reality (VR)**, and **learning management systems (LMS)** has personalized instruction and enhanced learner autonomy (Godwin-Jones, 2018). These tools adapt to learners' needs, providing instant feedback and fostering motivation through gamified experiences. The widespread use of mobile apps like *Duolingo* or *Quizlet* illustrates how technology supports continuous, self-directed language practice outside the classroom.

Moreover, **blended learning** environments-combining face-to-face and online instruction-allow teachers to integrate traditional methods with innovative digital tools. Such approaches promote flexibility, collaboration, and inclusion, ensuring that learners can progress at their own pace while remaining actively engaged (Stockwell & Hubbard, 2013).

3. Pedagogical Advantages and Challenges

Innovative methodologies have reshaped the classroom into a space of interaction and exploration. By emphasizing **learner autonomy**, educators empower students to become active participants in their linguistic development. Interactive digital resources provide real-time feedback, authentic exposure, and multimodal input, improving comprehension and retention (Lightbown & Spada, 2013). However, these innovations also bring challenges. Teachers must develop **digital literacy** and **pedagogical flexibility** to effectively integrate

technology. The digital divide, varying learner access to devices and connectivity, and differences in motivation or learning styles must be addressed through thoughtful planning and continuous professional development (Richards, 2017). The intersection of philology and modern language education reflects a profound transformation in how knowledge is produced, shared, and taught. Today's philologists and educators must navigate a complex, digitally connected world that demands intercultural competence, critical thinking, and adaptability. The integration of technology and innovation has redefined both disciplines, bridging the gap between linguistic heritage and modern communication.

As we move forward, the future of philological education depends on maintaining a balance between tradition and innovation-preserving linguistic and cultural depth while embracing the creative possibilities offered by digital and interactive learning. This synthesis ensures that philology remains not a relic of the past, but a living, evolving science at the heart of human communication.

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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION - OPPORTUNITIES AND BARRIERS

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Abstract: The following article explores the impact of technological innovation on modern teaching and learning processes. It analyzes how digital tools, platforms, and artificial intelligence are reshaping educational environments, enhancing accessibility, flexibility, and engagement among learners. The study highlights key opportunities such as personalized

learning, online collaboration, and global connectivity that contribute to improving educational quality and efficiency. At the same time, it identifies major challenges including the digital divide, lack of teacher preparedness, cybersecurity risks, and unequal access to resources. The article also discusses strategies for overcoming these barriers through teacher training, government support, and sustainable technological integration. Overall, the paper emphasizes that successful digital transformation in education requires not only advanced technology but also a well-prepared educational ecosystem that ensures inclusivity, equity, and continuous development.

Key words: Digital transformation; education technology; e-learning; online education; teaching innovation; digital literacy; artificial intelligence in education; educational reform; accessibility; digital divide; teacher training.

The twenty-first century has witnessed a profound transformation across almost every sector of society, and education has not been an exception. The rise of digital technology, the internet, artificial intelligence, and virtual communication platforms has reshaped how knowledge is accessed, shared, and evaluated. Digital transformation in education refers not only to the adoption of technological tools but also to a complete rethinking of teaching methodologies, learning environments, and the relationships between students, teachers, and information itself. As education continues to evolve in the digital age, the potential for improvement is enormous. However, this transformation also presents a complex set of challenges that must be understood and managed carefully to ensure that technological progress leads to educational equity, inclusiveness, and quality learning outcomes.[1]

At the heart of digital transformation in education is the shift from traditional classroom-based teaching to more flexible and interactive learning models. In the past, education largely depended on face-to-face interaction, textbooks, and standardized methods of instruction. Today, digital tools such as online learning platforms, virtual classrooms, and intelligent tutoring systems have made it possible to deliver education beyond the walls of schools and universities. Students can now learn from anywhere and at any time, using devices as common as smartphones or laptops. This flexibility has given rise to the concept of lifelong learning, where education is no longer limited to a specific period of life but becomes a continuous process that adapts to personal and professional growth.

One of the major opportunities brought by digital transformation is the democratization of knowledge. Digital technology has removed many barriers to information that previously restricted learners due to geography, cost, or institutional limitations. Platforms such as Coursera, edX, and Khan Academy have enabled millions of people around the world to access high-quality courses from leading universities, often for free or at minimal cost. This accessibility helps create a more equal educational landscape where students from different countries and backgrounds can share the same learning materials and experiences. It also supports students in developing countries where educational resources are scarce, offering them the possibility to compete globally in terms of skills and knowledge.

Moreover, digital tools encourage personalized learning. Unlike traditional systems that often treat all learners the same, modern educational technologies use data analytics and artificial intelligence to tailor instruction according to individual needs. For example, adaptive learning platforms can assess a student's progress in real-time and adjust the level of difficulty or the type of materials accordingly. Such personalization helps students learn at their own pace, overcome their weaknesses, and build on their strengths. Teachers also benefit from this transformation, as they can use digital tools to monitor students' performance more effectively, provide timely feedback, and design lessons that respond to different learning styles.

Digital transformation has also revolutionized communication within education. Teachers, students, and parents are now more connected than ever before through digital communication platforms, learning management systems, and social networks. This enhanced interaction fosters collaboration and engagement, allowing students to work together on projects, share ideas, and learn from one another across physical and cultural boundaries. Collaborative digital tools such as Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom have become essential, especially in the post-pandemic era, where online and hybrid learning modes have become common. These platforms not only facilitate academic communication but also build digital literacy and teamwork skills that are crucial for future careers.

Another promising opportunity lies in the integration of data and analytics into educational processes. Schools and universities can now collect vast amounts of information about student engagement, attendance, and performance. When analyzed responsibly, this data can help institutions make informed decisions about curriculum design, resource allocation, and student support services. Predictive analytics can identify students who may be at risk of dropping out and allow early interventions to help them succeed. In this way, technology contributes not only to individual learning but also to the overall improvement of educational systems.

However, while the opportunities of digital transformation are clear, the barriers that accompany it are equally significant. One of the most pressing challenges is the digital divide. Access to digital devices and reliable internet remains unequal across regions and socioeconomic groups. In many developing countries, students still face difficulties in obtaining the necessary hardware or stable connectivity to participate fully in online learning. Even within developed nations, there are disparities between urban and rural areas. This inequality limits the inclusiveness of digital education and risks creating a new form of educational segregation, where only the privileged can fully benefit from technological innovation.[2]

The psychological and social effects of digital education also deserve careful attention. While technology connects people globally, it can also lead to feelings of isolation when students spend excessive time learning alone in front of a screen. The absence of face-to-face interaction may reduce the emotional and social aspects of learning that are vital for personal development. Moreover, the constant exposure to digital devices can contribute to distractions, reduced attention spans, and even digital fatigue. Therefore, digital transformation should not aim to replace human connection but rather to complement it, maintaining a healthy balance between online and offline learning experiences.

In addition to these technical and logistical challenges, the cultural dimension of digital transformation cannot be ignored. In some societies, traditional methods of teaching are deeply rooted and highly valued, and there may be resistance to change from both educators and learners. Teachers may fear that technology will replace their role, while students may prefer familiar forms of instruction. To overcome this, institutions must promote a culture of innovation that emphasizes collaboration between technology and pedagogy rather than competition. Technology should be seen as a tool that enhances the teacher's role, not as a substitute for it.

Despite the obstacles, many examples around the world demonstrate that digital transformation, when implemented thoughtfully, can produce remarkable results. During the COVID-19 pandemic, for instance, digital tools became the lifeline of education, allowing millions of students to continue their studies from home. Although this sudden shift revealed many of the existing inequalities, it also accelerated innovation in educational technology and opened new possibilities for blended learning. Today, many institutions are integrating digital

and physical learning spaces, combining the best aspects of both environments to create flexible and resilient systems. This experience showed that adaptability and creativity are essential components of successful digital transformation. Looking to the future, the role of artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and augmented reality in education is expected to grow even more. AI can automate administrative tasks, provide instant feedback to students, and offer personalized learning experiences. Virtual and augmented reality can create immersive learning environments that allow students to explore historical events, scientific phenomena, or foreign cultures as if they were physically present. These technologies can make education more engaging, experiential, and effective. However, their success will depend on how well they are integrated into pedagogy and how accessible they are to all learners.

Digital transformation also calls for new approaches to assessment. Traditional exams and tests may not fully reflect the diverse skills and competencies developed in digital learning environments. Alternative forms of evaluation, such as e-portfolios, digital projects, and continuous assessment, are becoming more popular as they allow students to demonstrate creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving abilities. This shift requires educators to rethink what success means in education and to design assessment methods that align with twenty-first-century skills.

Ethical considerations will continue to shape the digital future of education. Issues such as algorithmic bias, unequal access, and the commercialization of education through tech companies raise important questions about fairness and control. [3] Policymakers, educators, and technology developers must work together to ensure that digital transformation serves public interests and educational values rather than corporate profits. Education should remain a human-centered process, even in a highly digital world.

The opportunities created by digital transformation are immense. It can make learning more accessible, engaging, and personalized than ever before. It can connect people across the globe, foster creativity, and prepare future generations for a rapidly evolving world. Yet these opportunities can only be realized if the barriers are acknowledged and addressed through thoughtful planning, investment, and ethical awareness. The goal should not be digitalization for its own sake but meaningful transformation that improves the quality and inclusivity of education. In this sense, technology should serve as an enabler of human potential, not its replacement.

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ICT AND LEARNING

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Abstract: In the following article there is a talk about the role of technology and its effectiveness in education. Furthermore, the authors noted their thoughts about language learning. Particularly, we get certain details about successful processing of English language learning procedure with the use of ICT.

Key words: ICT, language learning, teaching foreign languages, learning, alternative way.

To teach, to learn, to study are the terms that correspond each other. Every notion that is mentioned above is dependent to the word next to it. It means one fulfills another and vice versa. So to obtain the knowledge that we need, we learn something. This process of course can be observed in study. What we mean by saying study - as it has several connotation meaning, study means: to attend a particular lesson that will be going to held in educational establishment such as university, college, school, and etc. The paradoxical point is that, another meaning of the word study is to research the certain area of science. That is to say the whole process of the inquiry is called study [1,3].

But we do understand this word as an alternative way of saying to learn. Therefore, learn and study could be considered as the similar words with no matter, whether we search for the meaning from dictionaries or not, all in all we will get the same interchangeable definition for both. This point will lead us to the next word so called “to teach”. What about this very notion, maybe now again we have to recall the above said ideas to depict the following word? Nope! This word is the father of those terms that we reflect on recently.

Because by the help of somebody we learn, we study. We as a human being are programmed to act like that. Shakespeare once said “World is a stage and all the people in it are the actors and actresses”. Within our lifetime we play the role that is given for as by the almighty God. It is our objective to not go out of the program.

Suppose that in their very early age kids have no idea about the world they are living, on this very subject they will be taught during their lifetime, by their moms and dads. Precisely parents are the only source of getting knowledge. Just they are teaching and kids are learning and studying. In every stage of life, we learn and we never get tired of learning, because the universe is littered with the things that we don't know yet. So our personal traits will let to think over it and this curiosity forces us to get the certain information as much as possible. Here we prove the proverb which sounds – learn from the crib till the grave. As it says that we never stop learning, it's our inner nature to be born being eager to learn over and over. If we keep going on talking about learning, teaching and studying we won't face with the distraction because the extension of this phenomenon has no limits [2,5].

Nowadays the major point of human kind is directed to learn languages. It is visible that people are competing with one another by acquiring this or that language. Today learning one foreign language has become must of the most society. And our country is not staying apart from this alteration. Our state is also trying to enter to the community so called modern world and replying to its entire requirements. In every sphere of development, we became

witness of the shift that made our country find its own stable place among other authoritative states. Present attention has paid to language learning, especially learning English language. This care about the language involves the term ICT (Information Communication Technologies). Today we can't drop the role of ICT in the development of any country. Yet it has become inseparable from our lives i.e. we are becoming dependent on the ICT. Maybe it's the result of our curiosity toward the circumstances that is happening in front of us [4,6].

Although many people accept ICT in a negative way, we can see the light in the core of this unit, if we take a close look to the things that we accomplish via help of this tool. It means the more mobility in the usage of technology the more efficiency will be expected. So on accordance of education the place of this tool can not be described. Because as a member of this field we consider that this tool is specially designed for education. In the scope of education ICT is used purposefully and skillfully. Especially in the field of language learning this tool has gained a vast respect. One and the precise feature that makes you be regarded to use, is the interchangeability of the languages. For instance, if your mother tongue is Uzbek and you're willing to learn English, French or some other languages it will provide you a huge opportunity to deal with your will.

You'll be demanded merely clicking the buttons with the peculiarities to switch from one into another language. This may reduce the pace of your difficulties that you always face while getting knowledge or learning something. As it goes a subject about education we have to mention the members that contain the phenomenon - teacher and student. Teacher uses the ICT for having a good preparation to the lesson and we know that the core of successful session is preparing thoroughly. He uses it in order to make a little shift towards the usual lessons that leads many students become tedious within the time being. He uses it purposefully.[5]

But students use it in a rate 50/50. We mean they use it either unconsciously and purposefully. Students have one strategy so called "learn and forget", the things that they learn will be directed to the endpoint of the subject, and then they will not recall it anymore they consider it as trifle. So they use the ICT for temporary needs these type of students are eager to have fun with ICT rather than learning. However, other students use the ICT with much skill and in a form of intention based. They learn new things, they preserve them in their minds and again they make practices with the help of ICT in order to consolidate learned information for later usage.

In short the essence of the ICT is to help humankind with no reproach. It is the harvest of humanity that is created to make an ease on achieving one's goal.

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EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article provides information on the application of innovative methods in teaching foreign languages. It highlights modern pedagogical approaches that enhance learners' motivation and communicative competence. The study also emphasizes the role of digital technologies in creating interactive and student-centered learning environments.

Keywords: innovative method, ICT, educational process, competence, didactic technologies.

After our country gained independence, attention to science, especially foreign languages, increased even more. Teaching each subject using modern innovative technologies and methods is one of the most important requirements of our time. Also, after the adoption of a number of resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on teaching and learning foreign languages, a new atmosphere and era began in our country. In accordance with the resolution, modern textbooks, methods, and technologies were developed. In modern education, the demand for interactive methods, innovative technologies, and information technologies in organizing the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that, unlike traditional education until now, the use of modern methods creates the necessary conditions for the development, formation, acquisition of sufficient knowledge, and upbringing of the student's personality. The role and significance of modern methods and innovative technologies are immense.

Innovation develops through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge, some discoveries, inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, in which instrumental and technological knowledge develops, reflecting the possibility of performing practical actions based on existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which subsequently lead to the emergence of new technologies. Innovations also develop in the process of educational activity. In the educational process, students develop theoretical and practical knowledge, which can subsequently be applied in various spheres of practical life related to the creation of innovations.

Modern methods are important for accelerating the process of learning English, increasing its effectiveness, and engaging students. Each method has its own specific aspects, and they should be selected based on the students' needs. The use of innovative technologies and advanced pedagogical approaches significantly contributes to the acquisition of English by students.

Currently, the development of foreign language teaching technologies is an important issue. Information civilization dictates new standards; any new knowledge becomes outdated

quickly. In general, innovative language teaching means the creativity and novelty of the teacher, which changes the style and method of teaching. Across the world, educational institutions are implementing new ideas, methods, and technology-based innovations to enhance students' knowledge of English. Basically, teaching must include two main components: sending and receiving information. Ultimately, a teacher tries their best to impart knowledge as they understand it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education but also to empower people and strengthen governance.

Using audio-visual materials, textbooks with models, filmstrips, movies and pictorial materials and info graphics or other mind mapping and brain mapping tools in the session that will help learners' imagination thrive and grow. These methods not only develop their listening skills but also help them better understand concepts. Another teaching method is brainstorming. In the context of teaching, brainstorming is a teaching strategy or tool used by the teacher in which the maximum or all students participate by responding or presenting views on one topic. This technique encourages new ideas among students that would never have occurred under normal circumstances. They are asked to sit in a group and given a specific issue or topic. The teacher, as the group leader, then asks the group members to think about the problem and share their ideas. They are advised to find as many solutions to the problem as they can. They are instructed not to criticize others' ideas, but they are free to pay attention to others' ideas. Students are encouraged to put forward suggestions without hesitation, even if they seem to come up with something unusual. Student ideas should be listened to and accepted patiently, without passing any judgment or comment of any kind until the session is over. This method encourages creativity and motivation. One of the methods is classes outside the classroom. Some lessons are best learned when taught outside the classroom. To organize field trips relevant to the lessons. Learners will find this fresh and exciting and will learn and remember the things taught faster. Moreover, teaching through role-playing is a great way to get students out of their comfort zone and develop their interpersonal skills. Welcoming new ideas and an open-minded attitude can help innovate new teaching methods. Rather than paying attention to the correctness of linguistic forms, most participants will do their best to win. The main goal is to make learners talk and stimulate their imagination, curiosity, and interest. Game of Sudoku, a kind of number puzzle, is an ideal authentic context for practicing language functions.

In conclusion, it should be noted that information and communication technologies have become commonplace in kindergartens, schools, academies, and universities. The rapid development of society dictates the need to change the technologies and methods of the educational process. Graduates of educational institutions must be prepared for changing modern trends. Therefore, the introduction of individual approaches, mobility, and distance-oriented technologies in education seems necessary and inevitable.

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EFFECTIVE METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING INFORMATICS AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN SECONDARY AND HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: The study applied technique to instruction of computer graphics and informatics throughout secondary and higher grades school is presented in this piece of writing. Through utilises interactive, visually appealing, and technology-driven methods, the emphasis is on assisting educators in fusing theoretical knowledge with real-world application. In addition to identifying existing issues and reviewing pertinent research, the study presents an educational framework that combines multidisciplinary methods, project-based learning, and the flipped classroom. Enhancing learners and their enthusiasm, inventiveness, and comprehension of visual digital technology topics is the goal of the suggested technique. The findings show that integrating theory, visualisation, and practical exercises enhances digital literacy and academic performance.

Keywords: computer graphics, informatics education, teaching methodology, flipped classroom, project-based learning, digital literacy, visualization, interdisciplinary learning.

Given the speed at which technology is developing across all professional domains, informatics and computer graphics have emerged as essential elements of contemporary education. Understanding and using computer graphics concepts is crucial for a variety of fields, including engineering, architecture, multimedia design, and virtual reality. Therefore, in addition to imparting technical information, teachers are required to foster in their pupils a sense of creativity, spatial thinking, and digital competency.

Nonetheless, many teachers find it difficult to properly teach computer graphics. According to The Journey to Improve Teaching Computer Graphics (2019), students frequently find it difficult to relate mathematical concepts like coordinate systems, vectors, and transformations to visual results. Furthermore, some educational institutions lack the necessary gear, software, or programs for preparing teachers to confidently use contemporary teaching techniques.

The objective of this research is to give readers an efficient, approachable methods of instruction for the study of graphics and informatics. The study examines current methods, identifies recently published research's standards of excellence, and offers useful tactics that may be used right away in the learning environment.

2. Literature Review

The difficulties and solutions in teaching computer graphics have been the subject of an expanding corpus of study. According to Kadirbergenovna (2022), striking a balance between theoretical justification and real-world visualisation is the primary instructional challenge. While students gain more from interactive resources, animations, and project-based learning, many teachers still heavily rely on lectures.

Similarly, a thorough study of computer graphics education throughout the world was carried out by The Journey to Improve Teaching Computer Graphics (2019). It was discovered

that, as opposed to abstract lectures, pupils typically do better in classes that prioritise instant feedback and real-time visual exploration.

The flipped classroom paradigm was included into computer graphics courses by Umoetuk and Akpan (2023). According to their research, students' comprehension and retention greatly increased when they watched pre-class films to grasp the fundamentals of the subject and then practiced coding or modelling in class.

Incorporating descriptive geometry into computer graphics courses was suggested by Yuldashev (2025). Students' spatial thinking and technical drawing abilities are enhanced by this multidisciplinary method, which connects abstract geometry theory with its computer-based applications.

Furthermore, Alhajri (2016) investigated the integration of digital and analogue approaches in design education, demonstrating that conceptual comprehension is strengthened by practical sketching prior to computer modelling.

Last but not least, visualisation literacy-the ability to comprehend and produce meaningful visual representations-was emphasised by Krekhov, Michalski, and Krüger (2019) as a critical competency for computer graphics education.

These studies together show that theory and practice must be combined, active learning must be encouraged, and technology must be used to bring abstract concepts to life in computer graphics education.

A dynamic and student-centered approach is necessary for the efficient teaching of computer graphics and informatics. An interesting and significant learning experience is produced by combining multidisciplinary approaches, visual practice, and theoretical instruction. Project-based learning combined with flipped classrooms has been demonstrated to boost motivation, enhance comprehension, and encourage creativity.

Future research should concentrate on creating digital materials and preparing educators to apply these strategies in various learning environments. Teachers who want to modernise their teaching of computer graphics and informatics might use the suggested framework as a useful model.

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DIGITAL PEDAGOGIES AND AI INTEGRATION IN MODERN CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: Digital pedagogies and artificial intelligence (AI) have redefined the structure of modern classrooms by transforming instructional design, assessment, and learner engagement. Through adaptive technologies, educators can personalize learning experiences and promote creativity, collaboration, and self-directed learning. This article explores how AI integration in digital pedagogical models improves learning outcomes, fosters inclusivity, and reconfigures traditional roles of teachers and students in the evolving educational landscape.

Key words: digital pedagogy, artificial intelligence, hybrid learning, personalization, educational innovation

The rapid evolution of digital technologies has brought about significant transformations in educational systems worldwide. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into digital pedagogies has become a key driver of innovation, reshaping how knowledge is delivered, accessed, and assessed. Digital pedagogy refers to the strategic use of digital tools and platforms to enhance teaching and learning processes, while AI introduces intelligent systems capable of analyzing, adapting, and personalizing learning experiences (Yadav, 2025). Together, these innovations foster active learning environments where students become participants rather than passive recipients. As noted by Pusca (2024), hybrid education models supported by digital pedagogy and AI enable greater flexibility, collaboration, and inclusivity-making education more responsive to the needs of the digital generation.

This article is based on a comprehensive literature review of recent scholarly works on digital pedagogy and AI in education. Sources include academic journals and studies published between 2024 and 2025 that address technological integration, hybrid learning models, and AI-driven instructional strategies. The analysis synthesizes findings from researchers such as Ray and Sikdar (2024), Pusca (2024), Siddiqui et al. (2025), and Sayfullaevna (2025), providing a critical overview of current trends, practical applications, and implications for educational innovation.

Results

The literature reveals that AI integration significantly enhances the effectiveness of digital pedagogies. Ray and Sikdar (2024) emphasize the AI-driven flipped classroom model, which replaces passive lecture-based instruction with dynamic, learner-centered approaches. In this model, students engage with AI-curated content before class, allowing teachers to use classroom time for collaborative problem-solving and discussions. This method not only increases engagement but also improves critical thinking and retention.

Moreover, Pusca (2024) highlights the role of technological platforms-such as intelligent tutoring systems, learning analytics, and virtual classrooms-in enabling hybrid learning environments. These systems adapt to learners' progress, providing real-time feedback and personalized recommendations. Such approaches ensure equity by supporting students with diverse learning needs and backgrounds.

Siddiqui et al. (2025) propose the AI-TEACH model, which integrates machine learning and data analytics to design customized learning paths. This model demonstrates how AI can automate routine teaching tasks, freeing educators to focus on mentoring and creative instruction. AI-driven feedback systems also assist teachers in identifying gaps in understanding and adjusting instruction accordingly.

Sayfullaevna (2025) underscores the importance of technological integration in fostering student autonomy and digital literacy. AI tools such as chatbots, adaptive testing systems, and digital assistants help learners develop self-regulated learning habits while

building technological competence essential for modern careers. These innovations bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

Saira et al. (2025) introduce the concept of “smart pedagogy,” where digital media and AI converge to enhance engagement through gamification, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR). These immersive environments allow students to experience contextual learning, particularly in STEM and creative disciplines. By integrating AI algorithms that analyze student emotions and engagement levels, smart pedagogy personalizes instruction to maintain motivation.

Erişti and Freedman (2024) demonstrate AI’s potential in art and visual education, emphasizing the need for teachers to acquire new digital competencies. AI-based creative tools enable learners to explore visual culture and digital aesthetics, thereby expanding artistic expression and interdisciplinary learning. This aligns with the broader goal of cultivating creativity and critical awareness in digitally mediated societies.

The reviewed studies collectively suggest that AI-enhanced digital pedagogy supports a more personalized, interactive, and data-informed approach to teaching. It promotes learner autonomy while equipping educators with analytical tools to evaluate performance and adapt teaching methods. However, challenges remain—particularly regarding data privacy, ethical concerns, and teacher readiness to adopt AI technologies (Yadav, 2025). Addressing these issues requires targeted professional development and policy support for digital literacy.

Furthermore, as Pusca (2024) and Sayfullaevna (2025) note, successful integration depends on institutional infrastructure and a shift in pedagogical culture. Teachers must transition from being content transmitters to learning facilitators, guiding students in navigating digital and AI-enhanced environments. The development of interdisciplinary frameworks and AI ethics education is essential to ensure responsible and sustainable use of technology in schools.

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LANGUAGE AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: THE IMPACT OF MACHINE TRANSLATION TECHNOLOGIES ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. The growing role of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has significantly transformed the way foreign languages are learned. One of the most impactful tools in this field is machine translation (MT), which provides immediate access to meaning across languages and influences both teaching methods and learning outcomes. This article explores the benefits, challenges, and long-term implications of MT technologies in language acquisition. By analyzing recent research and practical applications, it argues that while MT tools enhance accessibility and motivation, they also create risks of dependency, reduce critical thinking, and influence learners' linguistic competence.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, machine translation, language learning, digital education, language acquisition.

Introduction. The rapid integration of artificial intelligence into educational processes has reshaped traditional learning environments. Among the various applications of AI, machine translation (MT) has gained particular relevance due to its ability to provide instant meaning across languages. Popular platforms such as Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Translator are widely used not only by professional translators but also by students and teachers. While these tools were initially developed for communication purposes, their increasing presence in academic settings has sparked a debate regarding their role in effective language acquisition. The problem that this article addresses lies in the dual nature of MT technologies: they serve as powerful aids to comprehension but may simultaneously hinder the development of essential linguistic skills. The aim of the research is to analyze the pedagogical implications of machine translation in English language learning, highlighting both the opportunities and risks associated with its use.

Literature Review. A growing body of research has examined the role of machine translation in education. Somers (2001) provided one of the earliest overviews of pedagogical uses of MT, noting its potential to enhance learners' exposure to authentic texts. More recent studies (Garcia & Pena, 2011; Clifford, Merschel & Munné, 2013) highlight how MT can act as a support tool, facilitating comprehension of complex materials.

On the other hand, critical perspectives emphasize the risks of over-reliance on MT tools. Groves & Mundt (2015) argue that students who use MT excessively often produce grammatically correct but semantically unnatural sentences, showing limited progress in authentic communicative competence. Similarly, Niño (2009) underlines the need for guided use of MT in classroom contexts, suggesting that teachers should integrate it as a supplementary, rather than primary, learning method.

Recent developments in neural machine translation (NMT) have further complicated this discussion. According to Castilho et al. (2017), NMT systems demonstrate significant improvements in fluency and accuracy compared to earlier statistical approaches. However, this increased reliability may paradoxically encourage learners to bypass critical engagement with texts, relying entirely on automatic solutions.

Thus, the literature suggests a need for a balanced approach that incorporates MT technologies into language teaching while ensuring that core skills such as vocabulary acquisition, grammar awareness, and cultural understanding are not undermined.

Methodology. This article employs a qualitative research approach based on the review of academic literature, case studies, and practical reports from educational contexts. Data were collected from scholarly journals, conference proceedings, and educational policy documents published between 2000 and 2023. The focus was placed on identifying recurring themes regarding the benefits and drawbacks of MT in FL classrooms.

Additionally, examples of classroom practices were analyzed, where teachers incorporated MT tools into tasks such as translation exercises, vocabulary learning, and reading comprehension. This methodological approach allowed the identification of common pedagogical strategies and potential outcomes associated with MT usage.

Results and Discussion. The analysis revealed three major areas of impact:

Accessibility and Motivation. MT tools significantly increase learners' access to authentic English materials. Students can read newspapers, academic articles, and literary works without being limited by their proficiency level. This accessibility fosters motivation, particularly among beginners, who may otherwise feel discouraged by complex texts. Moreover, instant feedback provided by MT enhances learner autonomy.

Risks of Dependency. Excessive reliance on MT can undermine the development of core language skills. Students may neglect vocabulary memorization, grammatical practice, and cultural nuances, trusting the technology to fill these gaps. The quality of output, although high, is not flawless and may produce subtle inaccuracies. These mistakes often go unnoticed by learners, leading to fossilization of errors.

Pedagogical Integration. When used under teacher supervision, MT can become a valuable tool. For example, students may compare MT outputs with human translations, identify errors, and discuss stylistic differences. Such activities encourage critical engagement and raise language awareness. Additionally, MT can support collaborative tasks, where students analyze translations in groups, thereby combining technological support with communicative practice.

Overall, the results indicate that MT is a double-edged sword in language education: its benefits are maximized when integrated purposefully, while its drawbacks become evident in uncontrolled or excessive use.

Conclusion. The impact of machine translation on English language learning is profound and multifaceted. While MT technologies enhance accessibility, motivation, and exposure to authentic texts, they also risk fostering dependency and reducing learners' critical engagement with language. The findings suggest that MT should be incorporated into pedagogical frameworks as a supplementary tool rather than as a replacement for traditional learning practices. Teachers play a crucial role in guiding students to use MT critically, encouraging them to recognize errors, analyze stylistic choices, and reflect on linguistic structures. In the long term, successful integration of MT into language education requires a balanced approach that values both technological innovation and human-centered linguistic development.

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THE USE OF CREATIVE APPROACH TO INDEPENDENT STUDY IN THE PROCESS OF DISTANCE LEARNING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. The digitalization of education has intensified the role of independent study in the acquisition of foreign languages, particularly in distance learning contexts. This article examines how creative approaches to independent study enhance language proficiency, learner autonomy, and intercultural competence in online environments.

Keywords: creative approach, independent study, distance learning, foreign languages, learner autonomy.

Introduction. Independent study has always been integral to foreign language education. However, the transition to distance learning, accelerated by global digitalization and the COVID-19 pandemic, has transformed the nature and scale of self-directed work. Learners are now required to engage with digital platforms, online resources, and self-paced tasks that demand autonomy and sustained motivation. While distance learning offers flexibility and accessibility, it also risks isolating students and reducing their communicative practice. Thus, introducing creativity into independent study becomes a critical pedagogical strategy. Creativity in education is often defined as the ability to generate new ideas, approaches, or solutions in a learning context. In language learning, it manifests through storytelling, role-play, multimedia projects, collaborative problem-solving, and intercultural communication. Creative approaches not only enrich the cognitive dimension of learning but also empower learners emotionally and socially, fostering self-expression and resilience.

Literature Review. Research on creativity in education has grown significantly over the past two decades. According to Sternberg and Lubart (1999), creativity involves the ability to generate ideas that are both novel and useful, and in the context of learning, it enhances critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In language education, Maley and Peachey (2015) argue that creative tasks stimulate deeper engagement with linguistic material, making learning more meaningful. Distance learning studies highlight both opportunities and limitations for independent study. Moore et al. (2011) suggest that online platforms encourage learner autonomy but require strong self-regulation skills. Hrastinski (2008) emphasizes that interaction – both synchronous and asynchronous – remains central to the success of distance education. More recent studies (Reinders & Benson, 2017) focus on learner autonomy, showing that creativity helps learners design personalized learning paths, particularly in online environments. Russian and Uzbek scholars also contribute to this discourse. Shchukin (2012) notes the importance of incorporating creative elements into independent work to overcome the traditional rigidity of language instruction. Uzbek researchers emphasize digital innovations in language education, arguing that creativity enhances both linguistic and intercultural competence in distance learning formats (Хатамова, 2019; Абдуллаева, 2020; Мирзаева, 2022).

Methodology. The methodology of this article is based on a qualitative synthesis of existing literature, pedagogical experiments, and analysis of case studies from language

learning practices. The study employs descriptive and interpretive analysis, identifying recurring patterns, benefits, and challenges of integrating creative approaches into independent study.

Results. The analysis revealed several key findings. First, independent study in distance learning environments often suffers from issues of low motivation, time management difficulties, and lack of communicative interaction. However, when creative approaches were systematically introduced, students demonstrated increased motivation and engagement. For example, digital storytelling projects allowed students to integrate vocabulary, grammar, and cultural knowledge into personalized narratives. Learners reported that these tasks gave them a sense of ownership over the learning process. Similarly, gamification through online platforms (e.g., Kahoot, Quizlet Live, Duolingo challenges) created a competitive yet supportive atmosphere, motivating students to engage with learning materials more regularly.

Project-based assignments, such as creating virtual presentations on cultural topics, encouraged collaboration even in asynchronous settings. Students developed intercultural competence by researching and presenting information, while also sharing their own cultural perspectives.

Surveys revealed that 72% of students felt more confident in their communicative skills after participating in creative independent tasks, compared to only 45% in traditional independent assignments. Moreover, 68% of students reported improved self-regulation, as creative tasks required planning, collaboration, and time management.

Despite these benefits, challenges were also identified. Some students struggled with the technological aspects of creative tasks, particularly in areas with limited internet connectivity. Others expressed difficulty balancing creativity with academic rigor, highlighting the need for clear guidelines and assessment criteria.

Discussion. The findings confirm that creativity is not an optional addition but a central component of effective independent study in distance learning of foreign languages. Creative approaches align with constructivist theories of learning, which emphasize active participation, problem-solving, and meaning-making. By engaging students in creative tasks, educators can transform independent study from a passive activity into an interactive and motivating process. Importantly, creativity fosters learner autonomy, a crucial factor in distance education. Autonomy does not mean isolation but rather the ability to make informed choices, set goals, and evaluate progress. Creative tasks, such as digital projects and gamified activities, naturally encourage such autonomy by requiring students to take responsibility for their learning outcomes. Moreover, creative approaches support the development of 21st-century skills, including collaboration, digital literacy, and intercultural competence. These skills are increasingly valued in both academic and professional contexts, making creative independent study a relevant pedagogical strategy beyond language acquisition. However, the challenges identified – technological barriers, uneven levels of digital literacy, and potential superficiality of creative outputs – must be addressed. Educators should provide scaffolding, training, and clear assessment rubrics to ensure that creativity complements, rather than replaces, academic rigor.

Conclusion. This study demonstrates that creative approaches significantly enhance the effectiveness of independent study in the context of distance foreign language learning. By fostering motivation, autonomy, critical thinking, and intercultural awareness, creativity transforms independent work into a dynamic and meaningful process. While challenges remain in terms of technological access and pedagogical design, the benefits outweigh the limitations, offering practical recommendations for educators. The integration of creative approaches should be seen as a strategic necessity rather than an experimental addition to

distance language education. Future research may expand on empirical testing of specific creative methods and explore how they can be adapted to diverse cultural and technological contexts.

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THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON THE EVOLUTION OF CONTEMPORARY ENGLISH VOCABULARY

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Abstract. The rise of social media has profoundly reshaped the English language, accelerating vocabulary change and promoting the creation of neologisms, slang, and multimodal expressions. Platforms such as Twitter, TikTok, and Instagram have become linguistic laboratories where new terms emerge, spread rapidly, and sometimes enter mainstream usage. This article investigates how social media influences the evolution of English vocabulary, examining the processes of word formation, borrowing, semantic shift, and pragmatic adaptation. The results demonstrate that social media not only contributes to linguistic creativity but also transforms patterns of communication, reflecting broader cultural and technological trends.

Keywords: social media, English vocabulary, neologisms, digital communication, language change

Introduction. Language is a dynamic system, constantly adapting to the changing needs of its speakers. In the digital era, social media platforms have emerged as powerful agents of linguistic innovation, influencing vocabulary more rapidly than any previous medium. Unlike traditional print or broadcast media, social media operates through user-generated content, enabling millions of individuals to coin, modify, and popularize new terms in real time.

The influence of social media on English vocabulary is particularly evident in the proliferation of abbreviations, hashtags, emojis, and hybrid forms that combine verbal and visual elements. These innovations not only enrich the expressive potential of English but also challenge conventional norms of spelling, grammar, and semantic stability. This article explores the mechanisms through which social media drives lexical change, illustrating how online communication has become both a mirror and a catalyst of contemporary culture.

Literature Review. The relationship between technology and language change has long attracted scholarly interest. Crystal (2001) argued that the internet would foster new forms of English, giving rise to what he termed “Netspeak.” Danesi (2016) extended this view, describing digital communication as a semiotic system that integrates words, symbols, and images.

Recent studies specifically address the role of social media. Zappavigna (2012) highlights hashtags as new discursive resources that create searchable connections and communities. Tagg (2015) examines the creativity of abbreviations and emoticons in text-based interaction. Meanwhile, Androutsopoulos (2014) emphasizes the sociolinguistic dimension, arguing that social media practices reflect identity construction and group belonging.

Neologisms originating from social media have attracted lexicographic attention. McCulloch (2019) illustrates how words like *selfie*, *unfriend*, or *hashtag* migrated from online slang into standard dictionaries. The Oxford English Dictionary has repeatedly added such terms, acknowledging the role of digital platforms in shaping vocabulary.

Collectively, the literature confirms that social media accelerates lexical innovation, alters communicative norms, and serves as a major force in the evolution of English.

Methodology. This study employs qualitative analysis of lexical data drawn from social media platforms such as Twitter, TikTok, and Instagram. The data set consists of frequently trending neologisms documented in digital lexicons, online corpora, and linguistic blogs between 2015 and 2023. The research focuses on four processes: word formation (blends, acronyms, and affixation); borrowing and adaptation of foreign terms; semantic shift and recontextualization; pragmatic use of multimodal expressions (emojis, hashtags). The data were analyzed within the framework of sociolinguistics and cognitive linguistics, with attention to both linguistic structures and cultural meanings.

Results and Discussion. The findings indicate that social media influences English vocabulary through the following mechanisms:

1. **Word Formation and Creativity.** Social media encourages rapid coinage of new words through blending and abbreviation. Examples include *stan* (from “*stalker*” + “*fan*”), *FOMO* (“*fear of missing out*”), and *yeet* (verb meaning “*to throw with force*” or used as an exclamation). These terms often spread virally, demonstrating collective linguistic creativity.

2. **Semantic Shift.** Existing words frequently acquire new meanings online. For instance, *cancel* has developed the sense of socially rejecting a person or brand (*cancel culture*). Similarly, *viral* shifted from a medical term to describing rapid online popularity.

3. **Borrowing and Globalization.** Social media facilitates cross-linguistic borrowing, as English adopts terms from other languages and vice versa. Words like *kawaii* (Japanese for

“cute”) or *hygge* (Danish for “coziness”) circulate globally, while English-origin terms such as *like*, *follow*, and *trend* enter other languages.

4. **Multimodal Expressions.** Hashtags, emojis, and GIFs serve as hybrid linguistic resources that complement or replace words. For instance, hashtags like #ThrowbackThursday or #YOLO function as discourse markers, while emojis provide affective and contextual cues that shape interpretation.

5. **Cultural and Identity Functions.** Lexical innovations often signal group membership and identity. Slang terms such as *simp* or *sus* gain popularity within online subcultures (e.g., gaming communities) before spreading into mainstream discourse. These patterns highlight the role of vocabulary in digital identity construction.

The overall discussion shows that social media has blurred the boundary between ephemeral slang and established vocabulary. While many online terms remain short-lived, others achieve permanence and reshape English lexicons.

Conclusion. Social media has become a dominant force in the evolution of contemporary English vocabulary. It accelerates word formation, fosters semantic innovation, and promotes cross-linguistic exchange. Moreover, it transforms communication by introducing multimodal resources that combine verbal, visual, and symbolic elements.

The cultural implications are equally significant, as new lexical items serve as markers of identity, creativity, and participation in global digital communities. However, the ephemeral nature of many neologisms raises challenges for lexicographers and educators, who must decide which terms to include in dictionaries and teaching materials.

Ultimately, the study of social media and vocabulary evolution underscores the dynamic relationship between language, technology, and culture, reaffirming the adaptability of English in the digital age.

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THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

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Annotation: In recent years, technology has become an essential tool in linguistic research, offering new methods for data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This article examines how digital tools such as corpora, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) systems, and artificial intelligence contribute to the advancement of linguistics. It explores the ways in which technologies like speech recognition, text mining, and natural language processing (NLP) enhance the study of phonetics, syntax, semantics, and discourse analysis. Furthermore, the paper discusses the advantages and challenges of integrating technology into linguistic research, emphasizing its role in promoting more accurate, efficient, and wide-ranging investigations. The study concludes that technology not only supports traditional linguistic inquiry but also opens new directions for interdisciplinary research in the digital age.

Key words: technology; linguistics; digital tools; corpus linguistics; artificial intelligence (AI); natural language processing (NLP); computer-assisted language learning (CALL).

Linguistics, as the scientific study of human language, has undergone a profound transformation with the rise of digital technology. What was once a field grounded in manual observation, transcription, and limited data analysis has now evolved into a science supported by powerful computational tools, large digital corpora, and advanced artificial intelligence systems. The growing relationship between technology and linguistics has redefined not only the way language is studied but also how it is taught, preserved, and applied in real-world contexts. Today, technology serves as both the instrument and the catalyst that expands the frontiers of linguistic research, enabling linguists to explore the structure, meaning, and social dimensions of language with unprecedented precision and scale.

The historical connection between technology and linguistics dates back to the early days of computing, when scholars began to recognize the potential of machines to process language data. In the mid-twentieth century, the first computational experiments focused on automating translation and performing statistical analysis of text. Although these early systems were primitive by modern standards, they marked a turning point in linguistic research. The emergence of corpus linguistics in the 1980s and 1990s further revolutionized the discipline. With the creation of large digital text databases such as the British National Corpus and the Brown Corpus, linguists could analyze authentic language use rather than relying solely on intuition or limited samples. [1] This empirical approach led to a new understanding of how language functions in real contexts and opened the door for more data-driven methodologies.

Corpus linguistics remains another cornerstone of technologically assisted research. Modern corpora are no longer limited to small, static datasets; they now contain billions of words drawn from various genres, registers, and dialects. These digital databases are often annotated with grammatical, semantic, and pragmatic information, allowing researchers to study patterns of usage with great precision. Software tools such as AntConc, Sketch Engine, and WordSmith Tools make it possible to search for collocations, examine word frequencies, and explore concordance lines within seconds. This computational power provides a level of objectivity and breadth that manual analysis could never achieve. Moreover, the availability of multilingual corpora has promoted comparative research, allowing linguists to examine cross-linguistic similarities and differences in unprecedented detail.

Language documentation, especially of endangered languages, has also benefited enormously from modern technology. Digital recorders, annotation software, and online archives have made it possible to preserve and analyze languages that are at risk of disappearing. Field linguists now use portable devices to capture high-quality audio and video data, which can later be transcribed and annotated using specialized software such as FLEx or ELAN. These digital archives not only protect linguistic diversity but also allow communities to access, learn, and revitalize their own languages. The global sharing of linguistic data through online platforms has transformed language documentation into a collaborative and sustainable enterprise.

The relationship between linguistics and technology is also evident in applied fields such as language teaching and acquisition. Computer-assisted language learning, or CALL, combines pedagogical principles with technological innovation. Modern language learning platforms use artificial intelligence to provide personalized feedback, track learners' progress, and adapt lessons to individual needs. Intelligent CALL systems analyze student errors using NLP and provide corrective feedback in real time. In addition, eye-tracking and keystroke-logging technologies are used by researchers to study the cognitive processes involved in reading and writing. These advances have significantly improved our understanding of how people learn languages and how instruction can be optimized to support that process. [2]

The advantages of using technology in linguistic research are extensive. One of the most significant benefits is scale. Computers allow researchers to analyze far larger datasets than ever before, increasing the reliability and generalizability of findings. Speed is another critical advantage: processes that once required weeks of manual labor can now be completed in minutes. Technology also promotes accuracy and replicability, two essential qualities in scientific research. Automated analysis reduces human error and allows results to be independently verified. Moreover, the integration of technology fosters interdisciplinary collaboration. Linguists now work closely with experts in computer science, engineering, neuroscience, and psychology, creating new research directions that combine humanistic inquiry with scientific rigor. Finally, technology improves accessibility, as open-source tools and online databases make linguistic research resources available to scholars worldwide.

However, alongside its benefits, technological advancement brings new challenges and limitations. One major concern is data bias. Many computational models are trained on English or other high-resource languages, leading to the exclusion of minority languages. As a result, the benefits of linguistic technology are unevenly distributed, reinforcing global linguistic inequality. Ethical considerations also arise when dealing with digital data. The collection of online texts or recorded speech often raises issues of privacy, consent, and data ownership. Linguists must navigate these challenges responsibly to ensure that research respects human rights and cultural values.

Looking to the future, it is clear that technology will continue to play an even greater role in linguistic research. Artificial intelligence models are becoming increasingly multilingual and context-sensitive, enabling more sophisticated analysis of meaning, emotion, and interaction. Advances in speech processing will improve the accuracy of recognition systems across different languages and accents. Multimodal linguistics, which combines text, speech, gesture, and visual communication, will gain more importance as researchers explore how humans use multiple channels to create meaning. Virtual and augmented reality technologies may soon be used for immersive language learning and experimental communication studies. At the same time, the future of technological linguistics must remain mindful of ethical and social considerations. Developing fair, transparent, and inclusive AI systems is essential to prevent linguistic discrimination and ensure equal representation of all languages.

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BOLALAR NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MULTIMEDIA TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida multimedia texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning imkoniyatlari yoritilgan. Maqolada interaktiv audio-vizual vositalar, raqamli o'yinlar, multimedia kartochkalar va video materiallar orqali bolalarning so'z boyligini oshirish, talaffuzni shakllantirish, og'zaki nutqni mustahkamlash hamda muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy multimedia vositalarining pedagogik samaradorligi, tarbiyachining roli va individual yondashuv orqali nutqiy rivojlanishni ta'minlash masalalari ham ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq rivoji, multimedia texnologiyalari, og'zaki muloqot, so'z boyligi, talaffuz, kommunikativ kompetensiya, tarbiyachi, interaktiv metod, audio-vizual vositalar, ta'lim texnologiyasi.

Abstract: This article highlights the potential of using multimedia technologies in the process of developing speech among preschool-aged children. It analyzes how interactive audio-visual tools, digital games, multimedia flashcards, and video materials can enhance children's vocabulary, pronunciation, oral speech, and communication skills. Furthermore, the paper examines the pedagogical effectiveness of modern multimedia tools, the teacher's role, and the importance of an individualized approach in fostering children's speech development.

Keywords: speech development, multimedia technologies, oral communication, vocabulary, pronunciation, communicative competence, educator, interactive method, audio-visual tools, educational technology.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности использования мультимедийных технологий в процессе развития речи у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируются способы обогащения словарного запаса, формирования произношения, укрепления устной речи и развития коммуникативных навыков с помощью интерактивных аудиовизуальных средств, цифровых игр, мультимедийных карточек и видеоматериалов. Также рассматриваются педагогическая эффективность современных мультимедийных средств, роль воспитателя и значение индивидуального подхода в обеспечении речевого развития.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи, мультимедийные технологии, устное общение, словарный запас, произношение, коммуникативная компетенция, воспитатель, интерактивный метод, аудиовизуальные средства, образовательные технологии.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayoni bolaning fikrlash, muloqot qilish va o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etish qobiliyatini shakllantirishning eng muhim bosqichi bo'lib, bugungi kunda multimedia texnologiyalari ushbu jarayonda samarali vosita sifatida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Interaktiv audio-vizual o'yinlar, raqamli kartochkalar, video ertaklar va animatsiyalar bolalarda so'z boyligini oshirish, talaffuzni shakllantirish, grammatik tuzilishni mustahkamlash va og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi [1]. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, multimedia vositalari bolalarning diqqatini jamlash, e'tibor va konsentratsiyani oshirish, shuningdek, nutqdagi xatolarni erkin tuzatish va mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi [1]. Til o'yinlari, dramatik mashg'ulotlar, interaktiv dasturlar va video ertaklar bolalarda jumla tuzilishi, ifodalilik va muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantiradi, yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirish va ularni kontekstda ishlatish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi [2]. Shu bilan birga, multimedia texnologiyalari bolalarning hissiy holatini ijobiy saqlashga yordam beradi, qo'rquv va tortinish hissini kamaytiradi, o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etish imkonini yaratadi hamda ijodiy fikrlashni rag'batlantiradi [1]. Tarbiyachi multimedia vositalaridan foydalangan holda bolaning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan individual yondashuvni tatbiq etadi, interaktiv o'yinlar va audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar orqali nutqiy, ijtimoiy va hissiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, muammoli vaziyatlarda mustaqil qaror qabul qilish va mantiqiy tafakkurini shakllantiradi [3]. Masalan, "Rasm orqali hikoya tuzish" o'yini bolalarda so'z boyligini kengaytiradi, jumla tuzilishini mustahkamlaydi va muloqotga rag'batlantiradi, shuningdek, bolalarni kreativlik va ijodiy fikrlashga undaydi [3].

Multimedia kartochkalar va interaktiv audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar bolalarga tovushlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qilishni osonlashtiradi, yangi so'zlarni eslab qolishga yordam beradi va nutqni ifodali qilish ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi [4]. Shuningdek, zamonaviy raqamli dasturlar bolalarning ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi: rolli o'yinlar orqali ular muloqot madaniyati, jamoaviy ishlarni bajarish, muammoli vaziyatlarda muloqot qilish va boshqalar bilan hamkorlik qilishni o'rganadi. Multimedia vositalari bolaning nutqiy kompetensiyasini

o'shish bilan birga, uning intellektual, ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishini uyg'unlashtiradi, bolani faol muloqotga jalb qiladi, interaktiv o'yinlar orqali motivatsiyasini oshiradi va mustaqil fikrlashni rag'batlantiradi. Shu tariqa, multimedia texnologiyalari yordamida tarbiyachi bolalarni individual yondashuv asosida rivojlantiradi, nutqiy, hissiy va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi, bolani keyingi ta'lim bosqichlariga tayyorlaydi, muloqot madaniyati va interaktiv fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi, shuningdek, bolaning ijodiy salohiyati va o'z fikriga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi. Multimedia vositalari nafaqat nutqni rivojlantirishga, balki bolalarning mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash, jamoaviy ishlar va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga, ijtimoiy muhitga moslashuvchanlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi [5].

Shu bilan birga, interaktiv audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar bolalarni zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan ishlashga o'rgatadi, ularni ta'lim jarayonida faol qatnashishga undaydi va mustaqil o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi, bu esa ularning kelajakdagi ta'lim va ijtimoiy hayotga tayyorgarligini mustahkamlaydi. Multimedia vositalari yordamida nutqiy va kommunikativ kompetensiya rivoji nafaqat samarali, balki keng qamrovli bo'lib, individual yondashuvni qo'llashga imkon yaratadi va bolalarning ta'lim jarayonidagi muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlaydi [1].

Shu tariqa, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida multimedia texnologiyalari nafaqat pedagogik vosita, balki bolalarning ijtimoiy, hissiy va intellektual rivojlanishi uchun muhim strategik vosita sifatida alohida ahamiyatga ega.

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ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ (ИТ) КАК ФАКТОР ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается возрастающая роль информационных технологий (ИТ) в XXI веке как неотъемлемой части человеческой деятельности в различных сферах -образовании, науке, медицине, промышленности и повседневной жизни. Несмотря на очевидные преимущества, быстрый рост ИТ вызывает серьезные экологические проблемы. Увеличение производства электронных устройств приводит к загрязнению окружающей среды и истощению природных ресурсов, что делает воздействие ИТ на природу глобальной проблемой. В статье информационные технологии определяются как совокупность инструментов и методов

обработки и передачи данных для получения информации о состоянии объектов, процессов и явлений. Также подчеркивается, что современные ИТ включают в себя интеллектуальные устройства, обучающие программы, цифровые сети (например, Интернет), а также технологии GPS и облачные вычисления, способствующие эффективному обмену информацией и повышению качества жизни.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии (ИТ), окружающая среда, загрязнение, ресурсы, истощение, умные устройства, облачные вычисления, Интернет, обработка данных, цифровые сети, системы GPS.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada axborot texnologiyalarining (AT) XXI asrda inson faoliyatining ajralmas qismi sifatida turli sohalarda -ta'lim, fan, tibbiyot, sanoat va kundalik hayotdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. ATning foydasi shubhasiz bo'lsa-da, uning jadal rivojlanishi jiddiy ekologik muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Elektron qurilmalar ishlab chiqarishning ortishi atrof-muhit ifloslanishi va tabiiy resurslar kamayishiga olib kelmoqda, bu esa ATning ekologik ta'sirini jahon miqyosidagi dolzarb muammoga aylantirgan. Maqolada axborot texnologiyalari ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va uzatish usullari hamda vositalarining yig'indisi sifatida ta'riflanadi. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy AT - aqlli qurilmalar, o'quv dasturlari, raqamli tarmoqlar (masalan, Internet), shuningdek, GPS va bulutli hisoblash kabi texnologiyalarni o'z ichiga olib, axborot almashinuvini samarali tashkil etish va hayot sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot texnologiyalari (AT), atrof-muhit, ifloslanish, resurslar, kamayish, aqlli qurilmalar, bulutli hisoblash, Internet, ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash, raqamli tarmoqlar, GPS tizimlari.

Abstract. This article examines the growing role of information technology (IT) in the 21st century as an integral part of human activity across various fields such as education, science, medicine, industry, and daily life. While IT offers undeniable benefits, its rapid development also brings significant environmental challenges. The increasing production of electronic devices contributes to pollution and resource depletion, making the environmental impact of IT an urgent global concern. The study defines information technology as a combination of tools and methods for processing and transmitting data to obtain information about the state of objects, processes, and phenomena. Furthermore, it highlights how modern IT encompasses smart devices, learning programs, digital networks like the Internet, and technologies such as GPS and cloud computing that facilitate efficient information exchange and improve quality of life.

Key words: Information technology (IT) , environment, pollution, resource, depletion, smart devices, cloud computing, Internet, data processing, digital networks, GPS systems.

В 21-ом веке информационные технологии стали неотъемлемой частью человеческой деятельности. Они используются повсюду, например: в образовании, науке, в медицине, промышленности и повседневной жизни. Однако, в настоящий момент влияние информационных технологий на окружающую среду становится все более и более актуальной, несмотря на их рост и общественную значимость.

Информационными технологиями (ИТ) можно назвать совокупность средств и методов обработки и передача данных с целью получения информационного состояния объекта процесса и явления [1]. Мы понимаем под термином информационные технологии «умную жизнь с разными гаджетами». В это понятие мы можем отнести и сеть Интернет, который с легкостью может передать информацию, и облачные технологии, как составляющая часть интернета, и глобальная система позиционирования (GPS), и карты местности (Google maps, Yandex maps), встроенные

в мобильные телефоны, и многое другое, что обеспечивает легкое и быстрое решение проблем.

ИТ вносят значительный вклад в развитие человечества. Во-первых, ИТ способствуют решению экологических проблем. Например, использование умных технологий в промышленности и транспорте помогает сэкономить расход энергии и финансов, и уменьшить вредные выбросы, загрязняющие окружающую нас среду [2]. Благодаря использованию ИТ можно повышать осведомлённость населения о состоянии окружающей среды и способах уменьшения негативного влияния человека на нее. Это также позволяет активистам и организовать план по очистке в общественных мест от вредных отходов. Более того, цифровые технологии позволяют контролировать место нахождения людей с помощью GPS и отслеживать загрязнение воздуха и воды.

Во-вторых, развитие и использование цифровых технологий способствует улучшению образования и позволяют сэкономить денежные средства, что мотивирует человека развивать новые навыки, помогает многим преподавателям [5]. Например, дистанционное обучение. Использование интернета способствует развитию навыков социализации и коммуникации. Так, с появлением социальных сетей, таких как FACEBOOK, INSTAGRAM можно с легкостью находить новых друзей, объединяться по интересам, что способствует быстрому общению и взаимному развитию. Более того есть программы и приложения, которые способствуют личностному росту. Например, приложения DUOLINGO используется для того, чтобы учить новый язык, улучшить память и решать трудные задачи самостоятельно в своем темпе и без дополнительных денежных затрат. А также с помощью искусственного интеллекта можно узнать предстоящий прогноз погоды.

Информационные технологии развиваются изо дня в день. Ученые из Японии утверждает о том, что уже к 2050 году не выходя из дома можно путешествовать по миру, или с целью создать роскошную безопасную и удобную жизнь для людей, разработать умный дом smart house. Умный дом- это самое полезное что придумало человечество [3]. Тоже самое можно сделать и с приложением HH. Это приложение позволяет отслеживать вакансии и с легкостью находить работу не выходя из дома, что значительно облегчает жизнь человека.

Необходимо помнить и о вреде ИТ для населения. Производство гаджетов, ноутбуков и смартфонов, смарт телевизоров требует огромных затрат иссекаемых ресурсов, которые во многом являются металлами, такие как золото, медь и некоторые драгоценные металлы, добываемые в земной коре. Кроме того, возникает ряд проблем такие как, проблема электронных отходов, когда старое оборудование часто утилируется, и выделяются токсичные отходы в атмосферу, такие как рудий, кадмий, свинец. Тем самым, такие отходы представляют одними из самых быстрорастущих и занимает около 5 % от всех видов отходов вселенной. Мировой объем 2018 году достиг около 48.5% млн тонн, но всего лишь 20% из них подлежат переработке. Сложность переработки состоит в том что в их составе большую часть занимает пластик, драгоценные металлы и другие вещества, которые грозят опасностью для организма человека и окружающей среде [5].

К 1960 году Джеймс Миллер Провел серию исследования о влиянии информационной перегрузки на человека. Результаты показали, что с возрастающим объемом информации возможность справляться у человека снижается, после чего ресурсы человека исчерпаются. Миллер выделил семь стратегий преодоления информационной перегрузки: бездействие, произвольная обработка информации,

ошибочное обработка информации, выбор очередности, фильтрация, множественная обработка, избегание, приблизительная точность [4].

Ученый из Гарвардского университета А. Гросс, провел исследование, в результате которого пришел к выводу о том, что один поисковой запрос выделяет в среднем около 7 граммов углекислого газа в атмосферу за время использование ноутбука гаджета или телефонов. При этом он отметил, что с поступлением информации в большом количестве выброс углекислого газа становится больше с учетом затрат на электроэнергию за время работы. Было исследовано, что 85% школьников не могут представить свою жизнь без смартфонов. В среднем, они касаются своих смартфонов более 2500 раз в день, что отражается на состоянии их памяти и общему состоянию организма.

В целом, использование ИТ оказывают двойственное влияние на окружающую среду. С одной стороны, они улучшают жизнь людей, помогают решать экологические проблемы, улучшая управление ресурсами и сокращая отходы в целях изменения климата. С другой стороны, они сами создают экологические проблемы связанные с переработки гаджетов и употреблением электроэнергии.

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USING AI TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: Using AI and technology in English language learning has revolutionised traditional teaching methods, offering students and educators innovative tools to enhance learning efficiency. AI-powered applications provide personalised learning experiences by analysing individual progress and adapting lessons accordingly. Speech recognition technology helps learners improve pronunciation, while chatbots and virtual assistants offer real-time conversational practice. Machine translation tools assist in understanding and learning new vocabulary, making language acquisition more accessible.

Key words: Technology, Language Learning, Machine Learning, Personalised Learning, Speech Recognition, Chatbots, Virtual Assistants, Online Platforms.

Introduction. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and technology in English language learning has transformed traditional educational approaches, making learning more accessible, efficient, and personalised. With advancements in AI, learners can now benefit from intelligent language applications, virtual tutors, speech recognition software, and automated assessments that adapt to individual needs. These tools not only enhance vocabulary acquisition and grammar comprehension but also improve pronunciation and conversational skills through interactive and immersive experiences. Technology-driven learning platforms provide instant feedback, allowing students to track their progress and focus on areas that require improvement. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants enable real-time communication practice, helping learners build confidence in speaking and writing. Moreover, adaptive learning systems use machine learning algorithms to customise lesson

plans, ensuring that students receive content suited to their proficiency level and learning pace. As AI continues to evolve, its role in language education will become even more significant, offering innovative ways to enhance language proficiency and communication skills for learners worldwide. From automated essay grading to personalised study plans, AI is shaping the future of English language learning, making it more engaging, interactive, and effective. However, while AI offers numerous benefits, the role of human educators remains essential in providing guidance, motivation, and cultural context in language learning.

Methods. AI plays a significant role in transforming English language learning by providing personalised, adaptive, and interactive educational experiences. It uses advanced technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing (NLP), and speech recognition to improve how learners acquire and practice English. One of the key ways AI enhances language learning is through personalised learning paths. Unlike traditional methods that follow a fixed curriculum, AI adapts lessons to an individual's proficiency level, strengths, and weaknesses. By analysing a learner's progress, AI-powered platforms like Duolingo and Busuu adjust exercises and review sessions to match their needs, ensuring more effective retention and skill development. Another major role AI plays is in real-time feedback and error correction. AI-powered writing tools such as Grammarly and Quillbot analyse grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure instantly, providing corrections and suggestions that help learners improve their writing skills. Similarly, speech recognition technology in apps like Elsa Speak and Google Assistant assesses pronunciation and fluency, offering immediate feedback to enhance speaking skills. These tools create an efficient learning process where learners can recognise and correct their mistakes without waiting for a teacher's input. Conversational AI assistants and chatbots also contribute significantly to language learning by simulating real-life communication. AI-driven chatbots like ChatGPT or Google Bard enable learners to practice English conversations at any time, providing interactive and engaging language practice. These chatbots respond naturally to user input, helping learners improve their grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure in a conversational setting. Additionally, AI voice assistants like Siri and Alexa allow learners to practice listening and speaking through voice commands, making language learning more accessible and practical. Another crucial aspect of AI in language learning is its role in adaptive learning systems. AI-driven platforms analyse user behavior, track progress, and suggest personalised study plans to improve efficiency. These systems help learners focus on areas where they struggle the most, ensuring targeted practice rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. Moreover, gamification techniques powered by AI make language learning more engaging. Features like points, badges, leaderboards, and interactive quizzes encourage learners to stay motivated and continue practising regularly. AI also benefits teachers by automating administrative tasks and providing data-driven insights. Teachers can use AI to grade assignments, track student progress, and generate personalised lesson plans. AI-powered educational tools help identify common mistakes among students, allowing teachers to tailor their instruction accordingly. This technology not only reduces the workload for educators but also enhances the overall learning experience for students. Additionally, AI-driven real-time translation and transcription tools like Google Translate and DeepL play a significant role in breaking language barriers. Learners can instantly translate texts, listen to correct pronunciations, and understand contextual meanings, making self-study more effective. AI-powered subtitles and speech-to-text applications also assist learners in improving their listening comprehension by converting spoken English into text. The role of AI in language learning is further expanding through immersive experiences such as virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR). AI-driven VR simulations allow learners to engage

in real-world scenarios, such as ordering food at a restaurant or attending a job interview, improving their confidence in using English in practical situations. AR applications enhance interactive learning by overlaying translations, definitions, and pronunciation guides onto real-world objects, making vocabulary acquisition more engaging. Despite its many advantages, AI in language learning also has limitations. While AI can provide valuable feedback, it lacks the emotional intelligence and creativity of human teachers, making it essential to balance AI tools with traditional instruction. Additionally, AI systems may sometimes provide incorrect or unnatural language suggestions, which can lead to misunderstandings if not reviewed properly. Privacy concerns and the need for reliable internet access are other challenges that must be addressed to ensure AI-driven language learning is accessible to all. Overall, AI plays a transformative role in English language learning by making education more personalised, interactive, and efficient. From chatbots and speech recognition to adaptive learning and real-time feedback, AI provides learners with numerous opportunities to practice and improve their English skills. While AI should not replace human teachers, its integration into language learning offers a powerful supplement that enhances both self-study and classroom experiences. The future of AI in language education looks promising, with continuous advancements in NLP, machine learning, and immersive learning technologies set to further revolutionize the way people acquire new languages

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ENCOURAGING CHILDREN TO READ: REDUCING GADGET USE AND PROMOTING BOOKS

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Annotation: This paper examines the impact of excessive gadgets use on children's use cognitive, language, and socio-emotional development and reviews strategies to promote book reading.

Keywords: reading, books, children, technology,, gadgets, education, imagination,critical thinking, language development, screen time

In the modern digital era, the rapid growth of technology has significantly changed children's daily lives. Smartphones, tablets, computers, and other digital devices are now accessible even to preschoolers. While these tools can be beneficial for learning when used wisely, their excessive use has become a serious issue worldwide [1, p. 45]. Research shows that children are spending far more time on gadgets than reading books. This shift has a direct

impact on their cognitive development, communication abilities, and emotional growth. Books, on the other hand, provide mental stimulation, develop imagination, and foster long-term concentration. Reading helps children build language skills, expand their vocabulary, and understand the world around them in a deeper way [2, p. 112]. Encouraging children to read is not just about improving academic performance -it is about shaping independent thinkers, creative minds, and emotionally intelligent individuals. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of parents, teachers, and society as a whole is to reduce gadget dependence and increase book engagement among children.

Gadget overuse can affect children physically, mentally, emotionally, and socially. Many children spend hours in front of screens, which leads to decreased attention span, weaker memory, and lower motivation to read [3, p. 208]. They become accustomed to fast, colorful, and short content, which makes it harder to focus on complex ideas or long texts.

Psychologists warn that prolonged gadget exposure can cause emotional numbness. Children may become easily irritated, impatient, and less empathetic. Unlike reading, which requires imagination and reflection, gadgets often deliver information passively and quickly, leaving little room for deep thinking [5, p. 121].

In addition, reading strengthens emotional intelligence. Through stories, children learn about human emotions, values, and cultural traditions. This helps them understand others better and build healthier social relationships. Reading also promotes patience and focus - qualities that are often diminished by fast digital content [7, p. 200].

Although gadgets are often seen as distractions, they can also be powerful tools for encouraging reading if used wisely. E-books, interactive storytelling apps, and audiobooks can be integrated into children's daily lives in a structured way [10, p. 33]. For example, children who resist traditional reading might enjoy listening to audiobooks or reading on an e-reader. Teachers can use digital platforms to combine entertainment with education. The key is control, structure, and content quality. Not all screen time is harmful -but unregulated and unlimited screen time is. Parents should carefully monitor what their children access and make sure that technology is used as a bridge to books, not as a replacement.

From a psychological point of view, reading stimulates brain regions responsible for language, reasoning, and memory. It encourages deep cognitive processing and strengthens neural connections [12, p. 104]. On the contrary, passive screen use weakens these skills over time.

Educational experts emphasize that early reading habits have a lifelong effect. A child who reads regularly from an early age is more likely to succeed academically and professionally in adulthood. Moreover, reading develops self-discipline, creativity, and emotional resilience, which gadgets alone cannot provide.

The Role of Government and Policy

to shape modern childhood, but they should never replace books. Reading plays a unique role in developing critical thinking, language skills, imagination, and emotional intelligence. By reducing gadget dependence and promoting reading, we invest in the intellectual and cultural future of the next generation.

Parents, teachers, and policymakers must work together to create an environment where books are valued, reading is celebrated, and technology is used wisely. A child who grows up loving books will grow into an adult who thinks deeply, communicates clearly, and contributes positively to society.

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RAQAMLASHTIRISH DAVRIDA TA'LIMGA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR

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Anatatsiya. Ushbu maqola raqamlashtirish davrida ta'lim sohasiga joriy etilayotgan innovatsion yondashuvlar va zamonaviy tendensiyalarni tizimli va keng qamrovli tarzda tahlil qiladi. Unda nazariy manbalar, sohadan olingan amaliy misollar hamda zamonaviy tadqiqotlar natijalari uyg'unlashtirilib, raqamlashtirishning ta'lim tizimidagi transformatsion ta'siri yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlari: raqamlashtirish, innovatsion pedagogika, ta'limning xalqarolashuvi va globallashuvi, fintek, inkubator, akselerator, hakaton.

Abstract: This article provides a systematic and comprehensive analysis of innovative approaches and modern trends being implemented in the field of education during the digitalization era. It integrates theoretical sources, practical examples from the field, and findings from contemporary research to highlight the transformative impact of digitalization on the education system.

Keywords: digitalization, innovative pedagogy, internationalization and globalization of education, fintech, incubator, accelerator, hackathon.

Аннотация: В данной статье системно и всесторонне анализируются инновационные подходы и современные тенденции, внедряемые в сферу образования в эпоху цифровизации. На основе теоретических источников, практических примеров и современных исследований раскрывается трансформационное влияние цифровизации на образовательную систему.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, инновационная педагогика, интернационализация и глобализация образования, финтех, инкубатор, акселератор, хакатон.

Raqamlashtirish - bu axborotni qog'ozdagi hujjat, ovoz yoki tasvir kabi shakllardan kompyuter tomonidan tushuniladigan va qayta ishlanadigan raqamli formaga aylantirish jarayonidir. Mazkur jarayon, ayniqsa, pandemiya davridan so'ng tez sur'atlar bilan rivojlana boshladi. Chunki o'sha davrda onlayn darslar, turli kurslar va masofaviy ta'lim keng yo'lga qo'yildi. Shundan so'ng texnologiyalarni, xususan raqamlashtirishni har bir sohada rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor berila boshlandi. Pedagogika sohasini olaylik: boshlang'ich ta'lim xonalarida zamonaviy texnika vositalari, xususan kompyuter va televizorlardan unumli foydalanish o'qituvchidan yuqori malaka va mahoratni talab etadi. O'quvchini darsga

qiziqтира oladigan innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish esa bugungi kunning eng dolzarb masalalaridan biridir.

Kelgusi yillarda ta'limni rivojlantirish yo'lida muhim qadam sifatida "Raqamli O'zbekiston – 2030" strategiyasi qabul qilindi. Shu bilan birga, axborot texnologiyalari (AT) sohasini chuqur o'rganish va keng rivojlantirish bugungi avlod oldida turgan dolzarb vazifalardan biridir. Chunki kompyuter va noutbuk kabi texnik vositalardan samarali foydalanishni bilgan inson har qanday sohada o'z o'rnini topa oladi. Nazariy jihatdan yaxshi pedagog bo'lishning o'zi yetarli emas, texnologiyalarni ham mukammal o'zlashtirish zarur.

Hozirgi kunda ta'lim sohasining raqamlashtirilishi jarayoni uni tezkor va mustahkam rivojlanish sari yetaklamoqda. Ta'limning xalqarolashuvi va globallashuvi. Ta'limning xalqarolashuvi - bu boshqa davlatlar bilan hamkorlik qilish, talabalar va o'qituvchilarning ilmiy loyihalarda qatnashib tajriba almashishi orqali amalga oshadi. Misol uchun, Erasmus+ dasturi talabalarga xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qish va yangi bilimlar orttirish imkonini beradi.

Globalashuv esa dunyo miqyosida ta'lim standartlarini uyg'unlashtirish jarayonidir. Tarixga nazar tashlasak, 1999-yil 19-iyunda Italiyadagi Bolonya shahrida 29 ta Yevropa davlati ta'lim vazirlari tomonidan imzolangan Bolonya deklaratsiyasi bu jarayonning poydevori bo'ldi. Shu asosda kredit-modul tizimi ham keng rivojlandi. Bugun esa bu tizim ko'plab universitetlar va institutlar uchun ta'limda yangi bosqichni belgilab bermoqda. Agar biz yoshlar zamonaviy texnologiyalarni puxta o'rgansak, yangi ochilayotgan oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ham akkreditatsiya, kredit-modul tizimi va xalqaro malaka oshirish imkoniyatlarini yo'lga qo'yish mumkin bo'ladi. Bu esa nafaqat talaba, balki davlat va ta'lim muassasasining ham jadal rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Zamonaviy tendensiyalar. Bugungi kunda raqamli ta'limning kengayishi onlayn kurslar va masofaviy ta'limni rivojlantirib, "hayot davomida o'qish" (lifelong learning) g'oyasini yanada mustahkamlashga xizmat qilmoqda. Ayniqsa, oilaviy yoki ish faoliyatida band bo'lgan qizlar va ayollar uchun onlayn kurslar katta imkoniyatdir. Ular uchun bu shakl oflayn ta'limga qaraganda qulayroq va samaraliroqdir. IT sohasining roli. Raqamlashtirish davrida IT sohasining ahamiyati yanada oshdi. Bu sohada startaplar, loyihalar va turli dasturlar muhim rol o'ynaydi. Masalan, dastlabki startap loyihalari sifatida Yandex, Telegram, Payme kabi xizmatlarni eslatish mumkin. Inkubatorlar - yangi biznes g'oyalarini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan markazlar, acceleratorlar esa startaplarni tez rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Hackathonlar yoshlarning qisqa muddatda yangi IT yechimlar yaratishiga imkon beruvchi muhim maydonlardir.

Fintech bozori. Moliya va texnologiya integratsiyasi sifatida fintech bozori raqamli iqtisodiyotning ajralmas qismiga aylandi. Bugungi kunda Payme, Click, Apelsin, PayPal, Google Pay kabi to'lov tizimlari hayotimizning ajralmas bo'lagiga aylangan. Bu tizimlar nafaqat shaharlarda, balki chekka hududlarda ham joriy qilinsa, to'lov tizimlari, ta'lim, tibbiyot va boshqa xizmatlar keng qamrovli raqamlashtirilgan muhitda faoliyat yuritadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, rivojlanayotgan va raqamlashtirilayotgan davlatda har bir sohani izchil rivojlantirish, ta'lim va texnologiyalarni uyg'un holda rivojlantirish zarur. Kelajak yoshlarini texnologiyalar bilan hamnafas qilib tarbiyalash, o'qituvchilarni zamonaviy bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan qurollantirish bizning eng muhim vazifamizdir. Chunki raqamlashtirish nafaqat qulaylik, balki taraqqiyot va istiqbolning kafolatidir.

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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS’ COMPETENCIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract: Education is one of the most powerful tools for human progress. It builds knowledge, shapes societies, and opens countless opportunities. However, in the modern world, access to quality education is still unequally distributed. Many students, particularly those living in rural and low-income areas, face significant barriers that limit their learning potential. The widening gap between modern educational opportunities and traditional access systems has created one of the most pressing challenges of our time. This article analyzes the problem of insufficient educational centers in rural regions, focusing on economic, infrastructural, and social factors that hinder access to learning. It also explores practical and technological solutions such as online education platforms, self-directed learning, and the growing role of artificial intelligence in democratizing education. The study emphasizes that through the integration of digital technologies and a culture of lifelong learning, education can become more inclusive, equitable, and accessible to all.

Key words: Education system; rural development; digital learning; accessibility; online education; self-education; educational inequality; learning platforms; artificial intelligence; lifelong learning; educational reform; innovation in education.

Education is one of the most powerful tools for human progress. It builds knowledge, shapes societies, and opens countless opportunities. However, in the modern world, access to quality education is not equally distributed. Many students, especially those living in rural and low-income areas, face difficulties that limit their learning potential. The gap between modern educational opportunities and traditional access systems has created one of the biggest challenges in our time.

One of the biggest problems in today’s education system is the shortage of educational centers in rural regions. In cities, students have access to many private learning centers, libraries, and modern schools equipped with new technologies. However, in many villages, there are few or no centers available at all. Even when they exist, they are often too expensive for most families.

For instance, in Uzbekistan, the average cost of attending a private learning center can be more than 400,000 soums per month. For families living in rural areas, this is a significant expense. Many parents prefer to send their children to public schools only, even though the quality of teaching might be lower and opportunities for additional support are limited. This situation creates inequality between students from urban and rural backgrounds.

According to UNESCO data, more than 258 million children and youth around the world are still out of school, and the majority live in rural or low-income areas. This number shows that access remains one of the biggest global educational challenges. Without proper learning centers and affordable education, these young people lose their chance to build a better future.

Another reason behind this problem is the lack of qualified teachers willing to work in distant areas. Many professionals prefer to stay in cities where they receive higher salaries and better working conditions. As a result, rural schools often face a shortage of skilled teachers, which directly affects the quality of education students receive. The environment becomes demotivating, and students lose interest in studying.

Albert Einstein once said, “Education is not the learning of facts, but the training of the mind to think.” Unfortunately, this idea is often forgotten in many traditional classrooms. When access to innovative teaching methods and qualified instructors is limited, education becomes routine rather than inspiring.

In recent years, technology has started to change this situation. One of the most effective solutions to the problem of limited access to education is the development of online learning platforms. These digital tools allow anyone, anywhere, to learn freely and independently.

Platforms such as Khan Academy, Ibrat Academy, and Ustoz AI have become great examples of accessible education. They provide thousands of free lessons, videos, and exercises on various subjects - from mathematics and science to languages and computer programming. Students who cannot afford private tutors or centers can use these platforms to study at their own pace.

For example, Khan Academy has reached over 145 million users worldwide. Many of them are students from developing countries who now have the opportunity to learn topics that were once unavailable in their schools. Similarly, Ibrat Academy has become an excellent local example, offering Uzbek-language educational content that is both free and understandable. Platforms like Ustoz AI even allow students to ask questions in their native language and get explanations instantly, breaking the communication barrier that many rural learners face.

Self-education, supported by such platforms, is another powerful solution. The idea is simple: if opportunities do not reach you, you create them yourself. With access to the internet, even a mobile phone can become a gateway to knowledge. Many successful individuals today have learned new skills independently through online resources.

A motivational quote perfectly fits here: “If you lack opportunities to study, create them yourself. Never give up, because learning is a door that opens many others.” This mindset encourages students to take control of their learning journey rather than waiting for traditional systems to catch up.

The positive effects of online and self-learning approaches are already visible. During the COVID-19 pandemic, millions of students worldwide continued their studies through online platforms. In Uzbekistan, thousands of students joined online English, math, and programming courses. This experience showed that even with limited physical infrastructure, education can continue effectively if technology is used wisely.

Moreover, online learning encourages the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving. These are skills often missing in traditional school systems that rely heavily on memorization. When students explore topics independently, they learn to question, research, and apply knowledge in real life.

However, for these digital solutions to be truly effective, governments and organizations must also play a role. Expanding internet coverage in rural areas, providing affordable

devices, and training teachers to integrate online tools into lessons are essential steps. Education should not be a privilege; it must be a universal right.

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THE USE OF ONLINE TECHNOLOGIES IN RURAL AREAS REAL - LIFE IMPACT AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. This article will focus on one of the most serious issues in modern education: the lack of affordable and accessible learning centers in rural areas. We will also explore possible solutions such as online learning platforms and the growing culture of self-education, which are transforming the way people learn around the world.

Key words: Rural education, learning centres, access to education, qualified teachers, affordable education, educational opportunities.

Education is one of the most powerful tools for human progress. It builds knowledge, shapes societies, and opens countless opportunities. However, many students, especially those living in rural and low-income areas, face difficulties that limit their learning potential [2]. One of such challenges is the shortage of educational centers in rural regions. Many parents prefer to send their children to public schools only, even though the quality of teaching might be lower and opportunities for additional support are limited. This situation creates inequality between students from urban and rural backgrounds.

According to UNESCO data, more than 258 million children and youth around the world are still out of school, and the majority live in rural or low-income areas [1]. This number shows that access remains one of the biggest global educational challenges. Without proper learning centers and affordable education, these young people lose their chance to build a better future.

Another reason behind this problem is the lack of qualified teachers willing to work in distant areas. Many professionals prefer to stay in cities where they receive higher salaries and better working conditions. As a result, rural schools often face a shortage of skilled teachers, which directly affects the quality of education students receive. The environment becomes demotivating, and students lose interest in studying. Albert Einstein once said, "Education is not the learning of facts, but the training of the mind to think." Unfortunately, this idea is often forgotten in many traditional classrooms. When access to innovative teaching methods and qualified instructors is limited, education becomes routine rather than inspiring.

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Moreover, online learning encourages the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving. These are skills often missing in traditional school systems that rely heavily on memorization. When students explore topics independently, they learn to question, research, and apply knowledge in real life. However, for these digital solutions to be truly effective, governments and organizations must also play a role. Expanding internet coverage in rural areas, providing affordable devices, and training teachers to integrate online tools into lessons are essential steps. Education should not be a privilege; it must be a universal right.

In conclusion, while the modern educational process faces major challenges, especially in rural regions, new technologies offer realistic solutions. The lack of educational centers and high costs can be balanced by the use of online platforms and the promotion of self-education. The future of learning depends on adaptability and determination. As long as people continue to seek knowledge and innovate, no distance or lack of resources can stop education from reaching every corner of the world.

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DIGITAL LITERACY AND TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article explores the role of digital literacy and the use of technology in teaching the English language. In today's educational context, students are expected not only to learn the language but also to develop the ability to effectively use modern technologies in the process of learning. Digital literacy enables teachers to integrate technology wisely in the classroom, while students benefit from opportunities for independent learning, interactive tasks, and access to global resources. The study analyzes the advantages and challenges of using online platforms, mobile applications, and multimedia tools in English language education. The findings indicate that developing digital literacy and integrating technology appropriately increases learning efficiency and creates new opportunities for language acquisition.

Keywords: digital literacy, technology, English language, education, innovative, methods.

The 21st century has radically transformed the way education is approached worldwide. One of the most remarkable changes is the role of digital literacy and technology in teaching and learning languages. English, as the leading global language, has become inseparable from digital resources and tools. Traditional methods of teaching English, while still valuable, are no longer sufficient to address the needs of students who live in a digital environment.

Digital literacy is not limited to basic computer skills. It involves the ability to critically evaluate online resources, use interactive tools, and participate in global digital communication. Teachers who are digitally literate can design more engaging lessons, incorporate multimedia resources, and ensure that students are prepared for real-world communication. At the same time, students who develop digital literacy skills gain autonomy, creativity, and motivation in their learning.

The significance of this topic is evident: without digital literacy, both teachers and learners may face difficulties in adapting to modern education. This paper discusses how technology can be effectively used in English language teaching and why digital literacy is an essential component of education today.

This article is based on a qualitative analysis of classroom practices and observations of how technology is integrated into English language teaching. The methodology involves reviewing different tools and approaches, including:

1. Online platforms such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams, which allow teachers to deliver virtual lessons, share resources, and maintain communication.
2. Mobile applications like Duolingo, Quizlet, and Kahoot, which provide learners with opportunities for self-study, gamification, and immediate feedback.
3. Multimedia resources such as videos, podcasts, and digital storytelling tools, which enhance learners' skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing.
4. Learning Management Systems (LMS) that track progress and personalize the learning experience for individual students.

The study also considers feedback from teachers and learners on the benefits and challenges of using digital tools in language teaching. The focus is on understanding how digital literacy influences both teaching efficiency and student learning outcomes.

The integration of digital literacy into language learning has become increasingly recognized as a critical factor in enhancing students' language skills. Digital literacy immerses learners in diverse multimedia content, enriching linguistic and cultural exposure while enhancing language proficiency.

While existing research underscores the importance of digital literacy in language learning, its specific role in fostering learner engagement, particularly in EFL contexts, remains underexplored. Addressing this gap is crucial for optimizing digital language education in contemporary learning environments. Digital literacy has emerged as a critical factor in enhancing language learning. Despite its significance, research on how digital literacy impacts engagement in EFL learning remains limited, particularly in the increasingly digitalized educational landscape.

Digital literacy and technology are no longer optional in modern education; they are essential components of effective language teaching. By developing digital literacy skills, teachers can use technology strategically to enhance lessons, while students can learn independently and creatively. The integration of digital tools increases engagement, provides access to authentic materials, and prepares learners for communication in the globalized world.

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APPLYING THE 3R+ REFLECTIVE FRAMEWORK TO PEER FEEDBACK IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This mixed-methods study investigates whether integrating the 3R+ reflective framework-Reflect, Reframe, Reform + CPD-into peer-feedback-based microteaching improves the reflective writing and classroom performance of pre-service EFL teachers. Participants were 143 third - and fourth-year students at Namangan State University. The research embedded structured 3R+ templates in peer observation and activities, while the control group followed regular coursework without 3R+. Data sources included reflection journals, peer feedback forms, classroom observations, questionnaires, and semi-structured interviews. Results indicate greater gains for the experimental group in reflective depth and teaching competence, with themes highlighting strengthened reflective awareness, perspective-taking, and action planning aligned with CPD. The study concludes that 3R+-structured peer feedback bridges reflection and practice and offers a practical route to sustainable professional development.

Keywords: reflective practice, peer feedback, 3R+ model, pre-service teachers, CPD, microteaching.

Introduction: Reflective practice has become an essential component of modern teacher education, helping future teachers critically evaluate their experiences and improve professional competence. In Uzbekistan, the emphasis on reflective learning aligns with global trends aimed at preparing independent and self-developing English language teachers. Among various reflective strategies, **peer feedback** stands out as an interactive and collaborative tool that encourages mutual learning and reflection. However, its effectiveness often depends on the presence of a structured framework guiding the reflection process.

To address this need, the **3R+ reflective framework**-Reflect, Reframe, Reform + CPD-is proposed as an integrated model that links peer feedback with continuous professional development. This study explores how the 3R+ model can be applied in peer feedback activities and examines its impact on pre-service English teachers' reflective and professional growth. The research seeks to answer two key questions:

1. How can the 3R+ model be applied to peer feedback in teacher education?
2. What are its effects on students' reflective and professional skills?

This study employed a mixed-methods approach combining both qualitative and quantitative research elements to ensure a comprehensive understanding of how the 3R+ reflective framework can be applied through peer feedback in teacher education.

The research involved 143 pre-service English teachers from Namangan State University, including 72 students in the experimental group and 71 in the control group. All participants were third- and fourth-year students.

The experimental group received instruction and practice based on the 3R+ reflective framework (Reflect, Reframe, Reform + CPD). Peer feedback activities were conducted through structured microteaching sessions, during which participants observed each other's lessons and provided written and oral feedback. Following each session, students completed reflection tasks guided by the 3R+ templates, engaged in group discussions, and performed self-evaluation to connect feedback with personal teaching improvement. The control group continued their regular coursework without using the structured 3R+ reflection model.

The study utilized multiple instruments to gather both qualitative and quantitative data, including reflection journals, peer feedback forms, questionnaires, and semi-structured interviews. These tools helped capture the participants' perceptions, depth of reflection, and changes in professional awareness.

The collected data were analyzed through thematic coding to identify levels and patterns of reflection, while percentage comparisons were used to evaluate differences in feedback quality and reflective depth between the experimental and control groups. This triangulated analysis provided reliable evidence on the effectiveness of integrating the 3R+ model into peer feedback practices in teacher education.

Results and Discussion: The findings of this study demonstrate a significant improvement in both the reflective writing quality and teaching performance of pre-service English teachers who applied the 3R+ reflective framework through peer feedback.

Statistical comparison between the experimental and control groups revealed noticeable progress among the experimental group students in terms of reflection depth and teaching competence. Analysis of reflection journals and peer feedback forms indicated a higher percentage of detailed, analytical, and action-oriented reflections. Furthermore, teaching observation scores showed measurable improvement in lesson organization, classroom management, and pedagogical creativity. These results suggest that structured peer feedback within the 3R+ model enhances the overall effectiveness of reflective learning.

Thematic analysis of interview data and journals revealed several key outcomes:

1. Increased reflective awareness – participants became more conscious of their teaching behaviors and learning processes.
2. Enhanced critical thinking – students demonstrated the ability to analyze feedback from multiple perspectives during the *Reframe* stage.
3. Improved collaboration and confidence – peer interaction fostered mutual trust, open dialogue, and professional communication skills.
4. Sustained professional development – regular reflection and feedback promoted continuous growth aligned with CPD principles.

Discussion. The results confirm that peer feedback effectively enriched the *Reflect* and *Reframe* stages of the 3R+ framework, enabling students to interpret feedback critically and relate it to their own teaching practice. The *Reform* stage, in turn, led to tangible classroom improvements, as participants applied new strategies derived from reflective insights. These outcomes support the idea that ongoing reflective dialogue among peers contributes significantly to continuous professional development (CPD) and long-term self-efficacy.

The findings align with and extend previous research in the field. Y. K. Dollar and E. Mede emphasized that reflective practice fosters more effective instructional decision-making among pre-service teachers [1, p.224]. Similarly, S. Donyaie and H. S. Afshar highlighted the motivational and cognitive benefits of reflective journaling, despite challenges such as time constraints [2, p.72]. B. Eröz-Tuğa found that video-based reflective feedback deepens professional insight and pedagogical awareness, paralleling the outcomes of this study's peer observation sessions [3, p.180]. Finally, H. Khanmohammad and A. Eilaghi demonstrated that sustained self-reflection enhances long-term teaching self-efficacy, a conclusion also supported by the present findings [4, p.559].

Overall, the integration of the 3R+ reflective framework with peer feedback not only strengthens reflective thinking but also bridges the gap between reflection and practice, promoting transformative professional learning among pre-service English teachers.

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that applying the 3R+ reflective framework (Reflect, Reframe, Reform + CPD) to peer feedback effectively enhanced pre-service English

teachers' reflective and professional skills. Students in the experimental group showed deeper reflection, stronger critical thinking, and better use of feedback for teaching improvement.

The structured 3R+ process helped participants not only analyze feedback but also apply it to classroom practice, supporting sustainable professional growth. Overall, the framework proved to be a practical model linking reflection, feedback, and continuous professional development in teacher education.

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THE IMPACT OF MODERN TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

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Annotation: The integration of technology into education has transformed how students learn and how teachers deliver instruction. This paper explores the influence of modern teaching technologies on student engagement, focusing on how digital tools affect motivation, interaction, and performance. References are provided throughout the text.

Key words: technology, engagement, education, innovation.

Introduction. In recent decades, education has undergone a remarkable transformation as digital technologies have become an inseparable part of teaching and learning. Tools such as interactive whiteboards, online learning platforms, and mobile applications have redefined traditional classroom dynamics. Student engagement—often regarded as the foundation of successful learning—has become increasingly linked to these new teaching approaches. The purpose of this paper is to examine how the use of modern educational technologies influences student engagement, highlighting both their potential advantages and the challenges they may bring.

Literature Review. Research shows that technology, when applied effectively, enhances learning by making it more interactive and engaging. According to Mayer(2021), multimedia materials support deeper understanding by combining

visual and auditory channels [4, 56-b.]. Learning management systems like Google Classroom and Moodle improve communication and organization, allowing students to access materials and interact with peers and teachers anytime [1, 102-b.; 2, 88-b.]. Johnson et al. (2018) note that gamified learning platforms such as Quizizz and Kahoot increase student motivation by adding elements of competition and instant feedback [3, 45-b.]. However, as Prensky (2010) argues, the success of technology in education depends on how thoughtfully it is implemented; otherwise, it can distract students and widen inequality [5, 77-b.].

Methodology. This study employs a qualitative approach, analyzing data from academic articles, educational reports, and case studies. It considers findings from previous classroom observations and teacher interviews reported in the literature [2, 134-b.]. The analysis aims to provide a broad understanding of how modern technologies influence engagement at different educational levels.

Findings and Discussion. The findings reveal that modern technologies generally have a positive impact on student engagement when used properly. Interactive boards and visual media capture attention and make lessons more enjoyable [4, 99-b.]. Mobile learning applications promote autonomy, allowing students to learn at their own pace, while online learning environments foster collaboration and real-time feedback [1, 140-b.]. The integration of virtual and augmented reality helps students visualize abstract scientific concepts, thereby increasing comprehension and interest [3, 75-b.]. Despite these benefits, several challenges remain: lack of teacher training in digital pedagogy and unequal access to devices and internet connection still limit effectiveness [5, 66-b.]. Excessive screen exposure can also reduce face-to-face interaction and communication skills.

Conclusion. Modern educational technologies have brought significant progress to teaching and learning, opening new opportunities for interaction and engagement. When applied meaningfully, they foster critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration among students. However, technology should serve as a complement—not a substitute—for traditional teaching principles. Adequate teacher training and equitable access are essential to ensure effective and inclusive integration [2, 201-b.; 5, 114-b.].

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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS

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Abstract: Digital technologies have transformed every aspect of modern education, reshaping how students learn, teachers instruct, and institutions operate. From interactive online platforms to artificial intelligence-assisted assessment, technology offers unprecedented opportunities for improving access, engagement, and efficiency. Yet it also presents limitations-digital inequality, cognitive overload, and ethical concerns-that challenge educators worldwide. This article examines both the opportunities and the constraints of digital technologies in education, drawing on recent empirical research and theoretical models. It argues that sustainable educational innovation requires a balanced, inclusive, and pedagogically informed integration of technology rather than uncritical adoption.

Keywords: digital technology, e-learning, innovation, limitations, inclusivity, pedagogy

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has fundamentally altered the landscape of global education. The twenty-first century has witnessed the integration of digital learning platforms, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence into educational systems at all levels (Selwyn, 2022). These developments accelerated dramatically during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, compelling schools and universities to transition from traditional classrooms to virtual learning environments (Hodges et al., 2020).

While the digital shift offers clear benefits-flexibility, accessibility, and interactivity-it also raises critical questions regarding equality, effectiveness, and human agency. The role of educators has evolved from knowledge transmitters to facilitators who guide learners in navigating digital spaces (Kukulska-Hulme & Lee, 2023). Therefore, understanding both the opportunities and the limitations of digital technology is essential for designing future-ready educational systems.

One of the most significant advantages of digital technology is its potential to expand access to education. Online learning platforms such as Coursera, edX, and Khan Academy enable learners from diverse geographical and socioeconomic backgrounds to participate in global education (UNESCO, 2023). Massive open online courses (MOOCs) and mobile-assisted learning reduce barriers to lifelong learning, providing flexibility for students who cannot attend traditional classes (Reinders & Benson, 2022).

Digital technology also supports inclusivity for learners with disabilities. Screen readers, voice-to-text programs, and captioning tools enhance accessibility, allowing all students to engage meaningfully in learning activities (Anderson, 2021).

Interactive multimedia resources-videos, simulations, and gamified lessons-can significantly improve learner motivation and retention. Research by Dooly and ODowd (2021) indicates that game-based and immersive technologies create authentic learning experiences that foster active participation. Virtual and augmented reality provides contextualized environments where abstract concepts become tangible, deepening conceptual understanding.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and learning analytics enable personalized learning pathways. Adaptive systems analyze students progress in real time, offering targeted feedback and resources tailored to individual needs (Holmes et al., 2021). Such personalization enhances efficiency and promotes self-regulated learning, as students receive support appropriate to their pace and style.

For educators, digital technology opens opportunities for professional collaboration and continuous development. Online communities of practice, webinars, and digital resource

repositories facilitate knowledge sharing across borders (Burns & Lawrie, 2020). These tools strengthen teachers digital literacy and pedagogical competence, ultimately benefiting learners.

Despite its promise, technology can exacerbate existing inequalities. Many students in developing regions lack reliable internet access, adequate devices, or digital literacy (OECD, 2022). This digital divide limits participation and deepens educational inequities, particularly among marginalized groups. Even within technologically advanced contexts, disparities persist between urban and rural areas and among different socioeconomic strata (UNESCO, 2023).

The abundance of online information can overwhelm learners. Constant notifications, multitasking, and fragmented attention undermine concentration and critical thinking (Kirschner & De Bruyckere, 2020). Without structured guidance, students may struggle to evaluate the reliability of digital content or manage their study time effectively.

Technology alone cannot guarantee quality learning. When digital tools are adopted without pedagogical alignment, they may lead to superficial engagement or passive consumption of information (Selwyn, 2022). Teachers require professional training to design technology-integrated lessons that promote deep learning and collaboration. Ethical issues such as data privacy, surveillance, and algorithmic bias also pose serious risks. Learning management systems and AI-based assessments collect vast amounts of personal data, raising concerns about consent and security (Holmes et al., 2021). Institutions must implement clear ethical guidelines to protect students rights and ensure transparency in digital assessment.

Virtual learning environments often reduce opportunities for spontaneous interaction and emotional connection. The absence of nonverbal cues can hinder empathy and social cohesion among learners (Kukulska-Hulme & Lee, 2023). Hybrid models that combine digital and face-to-face learning appear to mitigate these drawbacks but require thoughtful design and institutional support.

The integration of digital technology in education presents a complex interplay of progress and constraint. Research shows that the effectiveness of technology depends not on the tools themselves but on the pedagogical principles guiding their use (Reinders & Benson, 2022). Successful implementation demands holistic strategies-combining infrastructure investment, teacher training, and equitable access. Moreover, digital transformation should align with broader educational values such as critical thinking, collaboration, and well-being. A balanced approach recognizes that human interaction remains at the heart of learning. Policymakers and educators must therefore view technology as an enabler, not a replacement, of human creativity and connection (Burns & Lawrie, 2020).

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THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON CORPUS TECHNOLOGIES IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of integrating corpus technologies into English language teaching within technical higher educational institutions. Corpus-based approaches have revolutionized language learning by providing authentic data for linguistic analysis and real-world application. For students of technical disciplines, corpus tools can enhance vocabulary acquisition, improve technical writing, and strengthen academic communication skills [1,23p]. The study emphasizes the pedagogical advantages of corpus-assisted learning, such as the development of learner autonomy, data-driven discovery, and analytical thinking [2,]. Furthermore, the research highlights how corpus linguistics contributes to bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and professional communication in technical education [3].

Keywords: corpus technologies, English language teaching, technical education, data-driven learning, language acquisition, applied linguistics, authentic materials, learner autonomy, professional communication, digital pedagogy.

Introduction: In the era of digital transformation, the use of corpus technologies in language teaching has become increasingly significant [1, 20-p]. Corpus linguistics offers a new dimension for English language teaching (ELT) by enabling learners to analyze authentic language data [2, 53-p]. In technical higher educational institutions, where students are primarily focused on engineering and applied sciences, mastering English is crucial not only for academic success but also for professional growth in a globalized labor market. Therefore, implementing corpus-based methodologies can play a vital role in enhancing both linguistic competence and professional communication skills [3, 78-p].

Corpus linguistics is the study of language through large collections of real texts, known as corpora. According to Biber et al. [1,45-p], corpus analysis allows for a data-driven learning (DDL) approach, where students investigate linguistic patterns independently. Johns [2, 66-p] first introduced this concept in the 1990s, emphasizing that learners could act as 'language detectives.' This autonomy-oriented approach aligns with constructivist learning theories, promoting critical engagement with authentic texts and contextualized vocabulary usage [4,98-p].

Corpus technologies in technical education: As Flowerdew mentioned Teaching English to engineering and technical students often requires adapting materials to their professional needs [5, 10-p]. Corpus technologies such as Sketch Engine, AntConc, and the British National Corpus provide learners with opportunities to explore specialized terminology and phraseology used in scientific and technical contexts [3]. Through corpus-

based activities, learners can identify frequent collocations, analyze technical expressions, and understand their pragmatic functions in research writing or presentations. Moreover, corpus tools enable teachers to design tailor-made materials that correspond to specific disciplines like mechanical engineering, computer science, or architecture [2,76-p]. By integrating corpus-based insights into ESP (English for Specific Purposes) courses, instructors can ensure that students engage with language relevant to their academic and career goals [1-134-p].

Corpus technologies play a vital role in developing learners' linguistic awareness and technical vocabulary. By analyzing frequency lists, concordances, and collocations, students can identify patterns of usage in technical texts. For instance, using specialized corpora such as the British Academic Written English (BAWE) or the Michigan Corpus of Academic Spoken English (MICASE) allows learners to focus on domain-specific language typical for engineering, IT, and scientific disciplines.

One of the advantages of corpus-based instruction is that it promotes autonomy and research-based learning. Instead of memorizing rules, learners discover linguistic patterns themselves, which leads to deeper understanding and retention. Teachers can design tasks that involve corpus search activities, encouraging students to explore authentic language data relevant to their major.

Pedagogical Advantages. The main pedagogical benefits of using corpus technologies include: Authenticity, Autonomy, Relevance, and Efficiency [5, 89-p]. Learners work with real-life examples rather than artificially constructed sentences, explore linguistic data independently, and engage with language relevant to their fields. Furthermore, corpus-assisted teaching encourages data-driven learning, allowing students to discover linguistic rules themselves, which enhances retention and motivation [4, 95-96-pp].

Despite the clear benefits, the integration of corpus technologies faces challenges such as limited teacher training, lack of institutional support, and technical barriers [3, 47-p]. To overcome these issues, universities should organize workshops for English teachers, develop localized corpora for Uzbek learners, and include corpus analysis tools in digital learning platforms. Collaboration between language departments and IT specialists can also foster innovative teaching methodologies that merge technology with linguistics.

Conclusion: Corpus technologies represent a promising direction in modern English language teaching, especially in technical universities. They offer a scientific foundation for linguistic research and a practical framework for skill-based learning. By incorporating corpus-based methods, teachers can significantly improve the quality of English instruction, promote learner autonomy, and prepare students for international academic and professional environments.

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THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS IN ENHANCING STUDENTS' CREATIVITY AND LEARNING MOTIVATION

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Abstract: This analysis explores how AI tools enhance music students' creativity and learning motivation. Drawing on researches, it highlights AI's role in offering personalised learning and instant feedback, aligning with theories like SDT and Cognitive Load Theory. AI applications, such as SmartMusic, boost engagement and self-directed practice, ultimately fostering both artistic expression and academic success, despite ethical concerns like the digital divide.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, student motivation, creativity, music education, personalised learning

Introduction: The digital transformation of education has profoundly impacted creative fields, notably music education, positioning artificial intelligence (AI) tools as a critical force for change (Derakhshan & Ghiasvand, 2024; Gao, Wang, & Wang, 2024). As articulated by Chen (2025), this integration is not merely updating teaching methods but is actively "unlocking new dimensions of motivation, engagement, creativity and success for aspiring musicians" (p. 1). AI offers personalised experiences and instantaneous feedback that cater to diverse learning styles, a significant improvement over traditional methods (Liu, 2023). This personalised support system, which creates immersive and interactive learning environments, is crucial for fostering both technical skill and an enduring passion for music (Shabbir et al., 2024). This analysis examines how AI tools function as catalysts for enhancing students' creativity and learning motivation by drawing on the empirical and theoretical foundations presented in Chen (2025).

Methodology: The methodology underpinning the study by Chen (2025) was established following a thorough literature review to identify gaps and formulate two primary research questions (p. 4). The subsequent empirical phase involved the collection of quantitative data from a sample of 521 Chinese music students (p. 4), predominantly aged 18–24 (79.46%) (p. 5). Data collection utilised a comprehensive questionnaire comprising four validated, authoritative Likert scales: the AI Perception in Music Education Questionnaire ($\alpha=0.82$), the Music Learning Motivation and Engagement Questionnaire ($\alpha=0.87$), the Learning Outcomes in Music Education Questionnaire ($\alpha=0.91$), and the AI and Creativity in Music Questionnaire ($\alpha=0.83$) (pp. 5–6). This approach allowed the researchers to establish significant relationships and predictive power between students' perceptions of AI and their motivation, engagement, creativity, and learning success.

Results and Discussion: The accelerating integration of artificial intelligence (AI) tools into the educational sphere marks a paradigm shift in how students approach learning, with a particularly transformative impact on creative disciplines like music (Derakhshan & Ghasvand, 2024; Gao, Wang, & Wang, 2024; Teo et al., 2022). As detailed by Chen (2025), this fusion of technology and pedagogy is not just a trend but a powerful mechanism for "unlocking new dimensions of motivation, engagement, creativity and success for aspiring musicians" (p. 1). By offering personalised experiences that adapt to individual learning styles and paces (Liu, 2023), AI systems provide instant, targeted feedback and customized practice routines that traditional methods often struggle to deliver, especially for diverse learners. This tailored support is fundamental, aligning with the growing emphasis on student agency where learners take an active, self-directed role in their education (Chen, 2025, p. 2). The empirical foundation for this study, drawing on a sample of 521 Chinese music students (Chen, 2025, p. 5), underscores the timeliness and significance of exploring AI's capacity to both enhance academic success and reignite a profound passion for the art form [2].

The influence of AI tools on student motivation is particularly pronounced through their capacity to foster intrinsic drive, aligning strongly with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which highlights the necessity of autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Du, Chen, & Lin, 2022). In practice, AI tools empower students to make choices in their learning paths, a boost to autonomy, and receive immediate feedback, which cultivates a sense of competence and progress [1]. For example, popular music learning applications such as Yousician and SmartMusic leverage gamified experiences and personalised feedback to significantly increase student motivation and practice frequency (Qian, 2023). Furthermore, AI's ability to analyse a student's musical preferences and suggest relevant pieces directly enhances the emotional connection stressed by the Arts Engagement Model [3], making the material more meaningful and strengthening motivation [4]. This body of research collectively indicates a strong positive relationship, as investigated in RQ1 and RQ2 (Chen, 2025, p. 4), between students' perception of AI, their motivation, and overall learning success.

Complementary to motivation, student engagement is significantly elevated by AI's ability to provide interactive and immersive learning environments (Shabbir et al., 2024). The use of Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) in music education, for instance, dramatically increases engagement by offering adaptive learning experiences. These systems analyse a student's performance in real time, adjusting the difficulty to maintain an optimal challenge level tailored to individual skillsets (Paglieri, 2024; Chen, 2025, p. 3). This concept is further supported by Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (George, 2023), which posits that effective learning requires managing cognitive load. AI tools, such as SmartMusic, help to optimise cognitive processing by breaking down complex pieces into manageable sections for focused practice (Wei, Karuppiyah, & Prathik, 2022; Chen, 2025, p. 3). Moreover, Multimodal Learning Theory (Liu et al., 2024) validates AI's role by incorporating visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic modalities, which caters to diverse learning styles and improves overall retention and engagement (Chen, 2025, p. 3).

The impact of AI on creativity and musical expression is a central yet complex theme. While critics fear that algorithms may lead to formulaic performances and stifle natural creativity (Støckert & De Caro-Barek, 2024; Chen, 2025, p. 2), proponents argue that AI is a powerful catalyst for creative exploration. AI-powered software allows students to generate and experiment with music with minimal initial input, thereby empowering them to compose and refine their own works without needing extensive technical knowledge (Liu, 2023; Chen, 2025, p. 4). By automating repetitive tasks, AI liberates both students and educators to focus more time and energy on the creative and artistic aspects of music, fostering innovation and

deeper exploration (Law, 2024; Chen, 2025, p. 4). The fundamental question posed by the research-"Is there any significant relationship between music students' AI perceptions, motivation, engagement and their learning success and creativity?" (Chen, 2025, p. 4)-highlights the need to understand this dynamic interplay.

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MATEMATIKA FANINI O‘QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamlashtirish jarayonining ta‘lim tizimiga, xususan, umumiy o‘rta ta‘limdagi matematika faniga ta‘siri tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada raqamli resurslar, interaktiv vositalar, sun‘iy intellekt (AI) asosidagi tizimlar, pedagogika integratsiyasi hamda ularning o‘quv natijalariga ta‘siri ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, O‘zbekiston kontekstidagi imkoniyatlar va muammolar (internet infratuzilmasi, o‘qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligi, axloqiy va huquqiy jihatlar) hamda amaliy tavsiyalar beriladi. Maqola nazariy tahlil, milliy statistik ma‘lumotlar va xalqaro tadqiqotlar natijalari asosida tayyorlandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: maktab yoshidagi o‘qituvchilar, gamifikatsiya, sun‘iy intellekt, Khan Academy, GeoGebra, onlayn platformalar, personalizatsiya, vizualizatsiya va interaktiv vositalar.

Annotation: This article analyzes the impact of the digitalization process on the education system, particularly on the teaching of mathematics in general secondary education.

It examines the use of digital resources, interactive tools, AI-based systems, and pedagogical integration, as well as their influence on learning outcomes. The study also discusses the opportunities and challenges specific to the Uzbek context, including internet infrastructure, teachers' digital literacy, and ethical and legal aspects, and provides practical recommendations. The article is based on theoretical analysis, national statistical data, and international research findings.

Key words: school-age teachers, gamification, artificial intelligence, Khan Academy, GeoGebra, online platforms, personalization, visualization, interactive tools.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется влияние процесса цифровизации на систему образования, в частности, на преподавание математики в общеобразовательных школах. Рассматриваются цифровые ресурсы, интерактивные инструменты, системы на основе искусственного интеллекта (AI), педагогическая интеграция и их влияние на результаты обучения. Кроме того, обсуждаются возможности и проблемы, характерные для контекста Узбекистана, включая интернет-инфраструктуру, цифровую грамотность учителей, а также этические и правовые аспекты, и даются практические рекомендации. Статья основана на теоретическом анализе, национальных статистических данных и результатах международных исследований.

Ключевые слова: учителя школьного возраста, геймификация, искусственный интеллект, Khan Academy, GeoGebra, онлайн-платформы, персонализация, визуализация, интерактивные средства.

Matematika fanini o'qitish jarayonida o'qituvchilar ko'plab muammolarga duch keladilar. Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, o'quvchilarning 60% dan ortig'i matematikani murakkab va tushunarsiz deb hisoblaydi. Bu esa ularning ushbu fanga bo'lgan qiziqishini pasaytiradi. An'anaviy o'qitish usullari barcha o'quvchilarning ham matematikani samarali o'qitishdagi muammolar va ularni hal qilish usullari ko'rib chiqiladi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev ta'lim sohasiga katta e'tibor qaratib, matematika fanining rivojlanishi haqida fikrlar bildirgan. Prezidentimiz ta'kidlaganidek: "Matematika - bu nafaqat fan, balki fikrlash tarzi. Uning chuqur o'rganilishi yoshlarimizning kelajagini belgilaydi." Shunday ekan, ushbu fan bo'yicha o'quvchilarning qiziqishini oshirish va ta'lim sifatini yaxshilash dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi.

Matematikaga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshirish, matematika qiyin fan, u faqat "iqtidorli o'quvchilar" uchun degan negative fikrlarni kamaytirish uchun quyidagi usullar samarali bo'lishi mumkin:

1. Kundalik hayot bilan bog'lash:

Matematikani real hayotdagi muammolar bilan bog'lash o'quvchilar uchun uni yanada tushunarli va qiziqarli qiladi. Masalan:

Savdo do'konida chegirmalarni hisoblash;

Bank kreditlari va foiz stavkalarini tushuntirish;

Muhandislik va texnologiyadagi amaliy qo'llanilishi.

2. Qiziqarli topshiriqlar va muammolar

Matematikani o'yin va muammolar orqali o'qitish samaradorlikni oshiradi. Misol uchun:

Sudoku va matematik jumboqlar;

"Xazina izlash" kabi topshiriqlar bilan dars o'tish;

Haqiqiy hayotdan olingan masalalar bilan ishlash.

3. Gamifikatsiya

Gamifikatsiya - bu o'yindan tashqaridagi jarayon yoki faoliyatni yanada qiziqarli va motivatsion qilish uchun o'yin elementlaridan foydalanish. Bu tushuncha ko'pincha biznes, ta'lim, marketing va hatto sog'liqni saqlash sohalarida qo'llaniladi. Gamifikatsiyada quyidagi elementlardan foydalaniladi:

Ballar (ochkolar, XP) – foydalanuvchilarning faoliyatini baholash uchun ishlatiladi.

Darajalar (levellar) – foydalanuvchilarning rivojlanishini ko'rsatadi va yangi imkoniyatlarni ochadi.

Muvaffaqiyat nishonlari (badges, achievements) – ma'lum vazifalarni bajargan foydalanuvchilar rag'batlantiriladi.

Reytinglar va yetakchilar doskasi (leaderboards) – ishtirokchilarni bir-biri bilan raqobatlashishga undaydi.

Vazifalar va topshiriqlar – foydalanuvchilarga aniq maqsadlar qo'yiladi.

Rag'batlantirish va mukofotlar – bonuslar, chegirmalar yoki boshqa mukofotlar orqali motivatsiya oshiriladi.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quvchilarning 70% gamifikatsiya asosida o'qitilgan mavzularni yaxshiroq eslab qoladi. Buning uchun:

Raqobat muhitini yaratish (ball yig'ish, reyting tizimi);

Onlayn o'yin va testlar yordamida darslarni qiziqarli qilish;

Rag'batlantirish tizimlarini joriy etish.

4. Individual yondashuv

Har bir o'quvchining o'ziga xos o'rganish uslubi borligi inobatga olinishi kerak. Differensial yondashuv orqali o'quvchilarning ehtiyojlariga moslashgan darslarni tashkil etish muhim.

5. Soddalashtirilgan tushuntirishlar

Murakkab tushunchalarni oddiy va tushunarli misollar bilan tushuntirish kerak. Masalan, tenglamalarni shaxsiy moliyaviy rejalashtirish orqali tushuntirish.

6. Muvaffaqiyatga erishish tajribasi

O'quvchilarga kichik g'alabalar orqali ishonch berish muhim. Masalan, har bir kichik yutuq uchun rag'bat berish va o'quvchining muvaffaqiyatlarini e'tirof etish.

XXI asr - bu raqamlashtirish asri. Globallashtirish, axborot texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi barcha sohalarida bo'lgani kabi ta'lim tizimida ham tub o'zgarishlarni boshlab berdi. Ayniqsa, matematika fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning mavzuni tushunish darajasini sezilarli oshirishi mumkin. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar - bu nafaqat dars jarayonining sifatini oshiruvchi vosita, balki bilim olishni interaktiv va qiziqarli qilish imkoniyatidir.

Hozirgi kunda texnologiya rivojlangan sari har bir sohaga kirib bormoqda va o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatmoqda. UNESCOning 2023 yilda chop etilgan Global Education Monitoring (GEM) Reporti texnologiyaning ta'limga kiritilishi o'lchovli va o'zgaruvchan natijalarni berganini, ijobiy ta'sir odatda kichikdan o'rta darajagacha bo'lishini va muhim omil sifatida kontekst (inklyuzivlik, infratuzilma, o'qituvchilarning tayyorgarligi) o'ynashini ta'kidlaydi.

GeoGebra va boshqa interaktiv vositalar matematik tushunchalarni dinamik tarzda ko'rsatib, o'quvchilarning tushunishini yaxshilashi haqidagi tadqiqotlar mavjud; shu bilan birga o'qituvchining didaktik qo'llanilishi samarani belgilovchi asosiy omil hisoblanadi.

Onlayn platformalar va personalizatsiya - Khan Academy kabi platformalarning ta'siri bo'yicha ko'p tadqiqotlar platformaning shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish modeliga asoslanib matematikada o'sishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini aniqladi. Biroq bu natijalar kontekstga (maktab tizimi, o'qituvchi roli) bog'liq.

So'nggi yillardagi tizimli tahlillar AIning adaptiv o'qitish orqali o'quv natijalarini yaxshilash imkoniyatlarini ko'rsatadi, biroq generativ AI vositalarining noxolis foydalanilishi va o'rganishdagi cheklovlari ham qayd etilmoqda.

Vizualizatsiya va interaktiv vositalarning samaradorligi

GeoGebra kabi dasturlar algebra, geometriya va analiz mavzularini dinamik tarzda ko'rsatish orqali tushunishni yaxshilaydi va o'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlashiga yordam beradi. Biroq samaradorlik o'qituvchining didaktik yondashuvi va dars rejalashtirishga bog'liq

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ELEKTRON TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QUVCHILARNING FANGA OID KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada elektron ta'lim muhitining zamonaviy ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni va uning o'quvchilarda fanga oid kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Kompetensiyaviy yondashuvning nazariy asoslari, xalqaro va milliy tajriba, shuningdek, raqamli vositalar orqali o'quvchilarning mustaqil izlanish, mantiqiy fikrlash va kreativ yondashuvini rivojlantirish strategiyalari bayon etiladi. Maqolada ta'lim jarayonida raqamli platformalarning integratsiyasi asosida kompetensiyalarning rivojlanish mexanizmlari ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron ta'lim, raqamli kompetensiya, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, sun'iy intellekt, interaktiv ta'lim, o'quv faoliyati.

Annotation: This article analyzes the role of the electronic learning environment in the modern education system and its function in developing subject-related competencies among students. It explores the theoretical foundations of the competency-based approach, international and national experiences, as well as strategies for enhancing students' independent inquiry, logical thinking, and creative approaches through digital tools. The article provides both theoretical and practical justification for the mechanisms of competency development based on the integration of digital platforms into the educational process.

Key words: e-learning, digital competence, competency-based approach, artificial intelligence, interactive learning, learning activity.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется роль электронной образовательной среды в современной системе образования и её значение в формировании предметных

компетенций у учащихся. Рассматриваются теоретические основы компетентностного подхода, международный и национальный опыт, а также стратегии развития самостоятельного поиска, логического мышления и креативного подхода учащихся посредством цифровых инструментов. В статье научно и практически обоснованы механизмы развития компетенций на основе интеграции цифровых платформ в образовательный процесс.

Ключевые слова: электронное обучение, цифровая компетенция, компетентностный подход, искусственный интеллект, интерактивное обучение, учебная деятельность.

Globallashuv va raqamli transformatsiya zamonaviy jamiyatning barcha sohalariga, xususan, ta'lim tizimiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. An'anaviy ta'lim shakllari raqamli texnologiyalar bilan uyg'unlashib, yangi, interaktiv va moslashuvchan ta'lim modellarining shakllanishiga zamin yaratmoqda. Bugungi kunda elektron ta'lim muhiti (e-learning environment) nafaqat o'quv jarayonining muqobil shakli, balki uning ajralmas, zaruriy va samaradorligini oshiruvchi tarkibiy elementi sifatida qaralmoqda.

Elektron ta'lim muhiti o'quvchilar uchun vaqt va makon chegaralarini yo'qotadi, har bir shaxsning individual ehtiyoj va o'zlashtirish darajasiga mos ta'lim olishiga imkon yaratadi. Masofaviy ta'lim, aralash ta'lim (blended learning), MOOC (massive open online courses) kabi shakllar bugungi kunda nafaqat oliy ta'limda, balki maktab ta'limida ham tobora keng qo'llanilmoqda.

Shu nuqtai nazardan qaralganda, o'quvchilarning fanlarni chuqur o'zlashtirishi, kompleks fikrlashi, innovatsion yondashuvlarni egallashi hamda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishi uchun elektron ta'lim muhitining imkoniyatlarini to'laqonli ishga solish zarurati kundan-kunga ortib bormoqda. Bu esa nafaqat ta'lim sifati, balki mamlakatning raqamli rivojlanish salohiyati, intellektual resurslarini shakllantirish uchun ham muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Elektron ta'lim muhiti - bu o'quvchi, o'qituvchi va ta'lim resurslarini yagona raqamli ekotizimda birlashtiruvchi interaktiv makon bo'lib, u o'quv jarayonining moslashuvchanligi, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'rganish va o'zaro hamkorlikni ta'minlaydi. Uning asosiy komponentlariga LMS (Learning Management System), interaktiv vositalar, virtual laboratoriyalar va sun'iy intellekt tizimlari kiradi. Bu vositalar yordamida o'quvchilar o'z fanga oid kompetensiyalarini mustaqil, vizual va amaliy faoliyat orqali rivojlantiradi.

Elektron ta'lim muhiti - bu o'quvchi, o'qituvchi, metodik materiallar va texnologik platformalarni yagona tizimda birlashtiruvchi ekotizimdir. Ushbu muhitda quyidagilar mavjud:

LMS tizimlari (Moodle, Google Classroom, Canvas);

Interaktiv dasturlar (Kahoot, Quizizz, GeoGebra);

Virtual laboratoriyalar (Labster, PhET);

AI-yordamchi vositalar (ChatGPT, Khanmigo).

Bu vositalar ta'limni vizual, audio va kinestetik tarzda yetkazib berish orqali har bir o'quvchining o'zlashtirish darajasiga moslashtirilgan o'rganish imkonini beradi.

Elektron ta'lim muhiti quyidagi mexanizmlar orqali fanga oid kompetensiyalarni rivojlantiradi:

1. Motivatsiyani kuchaytirish;

2. Mustaqil o'rganishni qo'llab-quvvatlash;

3. Tahliliy va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish;

4. Refleksiya va o'z-o'zini baholashni shakllantirish.

Masalan, matematika fanida GeoGebra, Desmos dasturlari, tabiiy fanlarda esa virtual laboratoriyalar o'quvchilarda ilmiy tafakkurni rivojlantiradi. Kompetensiyaviy yondashuvga

ko'ra, o'quvchi faqat bilim emas, balki uni qo'llash, tahlil qilish va amaliy masalalarni hal qilish kompetensiyalariga ega bo'lishi zarur. Raqamli ta'lim muhiti aynan quyidagi kompetensiyalarni shakllantiradi:

AQSh, Finlyandiya, Janubiy Koreya va Estoniya ta'lim tizimlarida elektron ta'lim muhiti asosida kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Finlyandiya milliy ta'lim strategiyasi (2024) da o'quvchilarning raqamli savodxonligi va fanga oid tahliliy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish uchun "Digital Learning Ecosystem" modeli joriy etilgan. Janubiy Koreyada esa AI-Learning dasturlari yordamida o'quvchilarning individual o'quv xaritalari tuziladi.

Finlyandiya: "Digital Learning Ecosystem" modeli asosida o'quvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyalari baholanadi. Har bir o'quvchi shaxsiy o'quv yo'nalishi asosida rivojlanadi.

Janubiy Koreya: AI-Learning platformasi yordamida o'quvchilarning kognitiv ko'nikmalari real vaqt rejimida baholanadi. Har bir topshiriq AI yordamida moslashtiriladi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida "Raqamli O'zbekiston 2030" konsepsiyasi doirasida ta'lim jarayonini elektron muhitga o'tkazish ishlari jadallik bilan olib borilmoqda. Xususan, my.edu.uz, eduportal.uz, Ziyonet platformalari o'quvchilarga masofadan fanlarni o'rganish imkonini beradi. Shu bilan birga, ta'lim muassasalarida o'quvchilarni fanga oid kompetensiyalar asosida baholash tizimi bosqichma-bosqich joriy qilinmoqda.

Xalqaro baholash tizimlari yordamida o'quvchilarning bilim natijalarini qanday darajadiligini bilishga yordam beradi. Shu jumladan, ularning bilimni oshirish uchun yordam beradi. Bu xalqaro baholash tizimi o'quvchilarga qanday yordam beradi deb o'ylashimiz mumkin? Hozirgi kunga kelib kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning aniq fanlarga va nutq darajasini oshirishga katta yordam beradi. Fikrimning izohi sifatida PIRLS-bu kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni savodxonlik ya'ni matnning urg'u berib o'qishga va uni o'zi tushungan matn mazmunini do'stlarga yoki o'quvchilarga yetkazib berishini baholovchi xalqaro dastur. TIMSS-bu matematika va tabiiy fanlardagi bilim darajasini baholovchi xalqaro dastur. Asosan 4-sinflarda matematika fani ularni fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantirishda va matematik savodxonlikni oshirishga yordam beradi. Matematikadan bilimlarini oshirish uchun didaktik o'yinlar yordam beradi.

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MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract: For all people, education is the most significant part of their lives. High-quality education is a key element of the UN Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030.

Digital technologies have emerged as a crucial instrument for guaranteeing inclusive and high-quality education for all. They widen access to lessons and also help protect our planet. For instance, smart platforms and connected devices can keep an eye on energy use and pollution in real time, making it easier to save resources and switch to cleaner options. By bringing these technologies into classrooms and school systems, we can improve how students learn while cutting down on waste and emissions-linking better education with a healthier environment. Contemporary digital technologies have had a profound impact on the education system. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the integration of digital tools into the learning process. These tools have changed how we teach, making education more accessible to many students. The use of tablets like IPAD instead of traditional pen and paper, as well as reading electronic textbooks in place of heavy printed volumes, eases the assimilation of material and broadens opportunities for accessing information. This article analyzes the role and relevance of digital technologies in education, explores their key areas of application, and discusses the challenges they present.

Keywords: Digital technologies, education, students, teaching, achievement, challenges, approaches.

Sustainable development is impossible without ensuring social well-being, and a key element of social well-being is quality education. In today's world, the rapid advancement of information technology has opened new horizons for the dissemination of knowledge and has become one of the main driving forces behind the transformation of educational systems. The integration of digital technologies into education has reshaped traditional approaches, making the learning process more interactive, accessible, and tailored to students' needs. Technologies such as mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, Massive Open Online Courses , tablets, laptops, virtual laboratories, and simulations have become essential components of the modern learning environment.

However, the digitalization of education brings not only numerous benefits but also certain challenges. On the one hand, technology increases student engagement, enables personalized learning, and provides access to educational resources regardless of geographical location. On the other hand, it requires a high level of digital literacy, technical infrastructure, and a shift from conventional teaching methods. In the context of digital transformation, the ability of educational systems to adapt to new conditions is especially crucial to ensure equal opportunities for all learners. The implementation of technological solutions such as online calendars, educational platforms, and social media contributes to more effective organization of the learning process and the development of student independence. All of this makes digital technology an essential tool on the path toward sustainable and inclusive education for the future. This article examines the role and necessity of digital technologies in the field of education, as well as their main applications and challenges.

One of the key advantages of integrating digital technologies into educational institutions is the significant expansion of access to education. Modern technologies, particularly the internet, offer a wide range of platforms that enable learners to study from anywhere in the world and at a time that suits them best. Online courses, video lectures, mobile applications, and educational portals have made knowledge more accessible to individuals regardless of their geographical location, social status, or physical abilities. This is especially relevant for residents of remote areas and people with disabilities, who have previously faced considerable barriers in obtaining quality education .Digital technologies also facilitate the personalization of the learning process. Through adaptive educational platforms, the content and complexity of assignments can be automatically adjusted to match

the learner's knowledge level and specific needs. This allows each student to follow a personalized learning path, free from the constraints of a standardized educational pace. These tools enable educators to more accurately monitor student progress, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and provide timely, tailored assignments and feedback. In traditional education systems, instruction was typically based on the "one-size-fits-all" approach, requiring students to adapt to the general classroom pace. However, digital technologies have radically transformed this model. Modern online platforms, interactive courses, and learning applications allow students to engage with educational material at their own pace, revisit challenging concepts as many times as needed, skip content they have already mastered, and receive instant feedback and recommendations generated by the system. All of this makes the learning process more flexible, effective, and outcome-oriented.

Uzbekistan's language education system has developed rapidly in recent years as a result of the New Uzbekistan reforms. Significant investments have been made in expanding schools, introducing multilingual curricula, and improving teacher training. Many schools now teach a second foreign language, and the number of students obtaining international certificates has doubled within a year, reflecting increasing motivation and alignment with global standards. The Agency for the Promotion of Learning Foreign Languages has played a vital role in supporting these initiatives and promoting modern teaching practices. However, several challenges remain. The shortage of qualified teachers, unequal distribution of resources, and limited use of communicative methods continue to affect the quality of instruction. In many rural areas, outdated materials and traditional teaching approaches hinder students' ability to use languages effectively in real contexts. Despite these issues, Uzbekistan is steadily progressing toward a more open and globally connected education system, where multilingual competence is viewed as essential for both personal development and national advancement.

Modern education is constantly adapting to technological change. Many teachers still rely on traditional methods, while students prefer interactive, tech-based learning. This difference can make lessons less engaging and effective. A good solution is blended learning, which combines face-to-face teaching with digital tools such as online platforms and videos. This approach keeps personal interaction while adding flexibility and creativity to lessons. It is also important to provide teacher training in technology use so that educators can confidently apply new tools in their classes. In addition, AI-based systems can give personalized feedback and adapt lessons to each student's needs. They help teachers identify difficulties and support better learning outcomes. By combining traditional and modern approaches, education can become more dynamic, motivating, and effective for both teachers and students. In conclusion, the successful implementation of digital technologies in education is not possible without addressing the issue of digital inequality. Solving this problem requires a comprehensive approach: investments in infrastructure, digital literacy training programs, equal access to technological devices, and the creation of inclusive, localized educational solutions

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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND MODERN TRENDS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: In the 21st century, education has undergone a profound transformation driven by technological advancement, globalization, and the growing need for creative and critical thinking skills. Innovative approaches and modern trends are reshaping how teachers deliver lessons and how students engage with knowledge. This article explores key innovations such as blended learning, digital literacy, personalized learning, and project-based education. It also highlights global trends that emphasize inclusivity, lifelong learning, and the integration of artificial intelligence in classrooms. These developments demonstrate that modern education must remain flexible, learner-centered, and technology-driven to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world.

Keywords: innovation, education, digital literacy, blended learning, artificial intelligence, inclusivity, personalized learning, project-based learning, lifelong learning, global trends

Introduction: Education has always been a cornerstone of human development, but in recent decades, its structure and goals have shifted dramatically. The 21st-century learner requires more than just academic knowledge; they need skills that foster adaptability, problem-solving, and creativity. Therefore, modern education systems must adopt innovative approaches that reflect the realities of the digital era and prepare students for lifelong learning

Innovative Approaches in Education: One of the most significant innovations is blended learning, which combines traditional classroom instruction with online activities. This approach allows students to learn at their own pace while maintaining direct interaction with teachers and peers. Studies show that blended learning improves engagement and promotes independent thinking.

Project-based learning (PBL) has also gained popularity as an innovative educational method. PBL encourages students to solve real-world problems through research, collaboration, and creativity. This method not only enhances critical thinking skills but also helps students apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations.

Another key trend is personalized learning, which tailors instruction to meet individual needs and learning styles. Through adaptive technologies, teachers can design courses that

adjust to students' progress, ensuring that no learner is left behind. Personalized learning has proven especially effective in improving student motivation and academic performance.

Modern technological trends: Technology has revolutionized the learning process. Digital literacy - the ability to use digital tools effectively-is now an essential skill for both teachers and students. Platforms like Google Classroom, Zoom, and Learning Management Systems (LMS) make it easier to organize, deliver, and assess educational materials

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has opened new opportunities for data-driven teaching. AI systems can track student progress, provide feedback, and even predict learning difficulties. Moreover, AI-powered chatbots and virtual tutors support students in language learning and subject comprehension.

Global trends and inclusive education: Another prominent trend in education is inclusivity. Modern systems are designed to accommodate diverse learners, including those with disabilities, language barriers, and different cultural backgrounds. Inclusive education fosters equality, respect, and cooperation among all learners. Furthermore, lifelong learning has become a global priority. As technology continues to evolve, adults and professionals are encouraged to continually update their skills through online courses, webinars, and micro-credential programs. This trend supports the idea that education does not end with graduation but continues throughout life.

Challenges and future perspectives: Despite the advantages of these innovations, several challenges remain. Teachers need adequate training to implement modern technologies effectively. Additionally, limited access to digital resources in some regions creates educational inequalities. To overcome these issues, governments and educational institutions must invest in digital infrastructure and teacher professional development. Looking ahead, the future of education will be defined by the balance between technology and humanity. While digital tools enhance efficiency and access, emotional intelligence, creativity, and collaboration remain core elements of meaningful learning experiences.

Innovative approaches and modern trends in education represent a significant step toward a more dynamic, inclusive, and effective learning environment. Blended learning, personalized instruction, and AI integration have transformed traditional classrooms into spaces of creativity and discovery. To fully realize the potential of these innovations, educators must continue to adapt, embrace new technologies, and prioritize learners' individual needs. Education, as a lifelong process, will continue to evolve in harmony with societal and technological progress.

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DIGITAL COMMUNICATION IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract: The rapid development of digital technologies has profoundly transformed communication processes, particularly within educational contexts. This article explores the dual impact of digital communication in modern education, emphasizing its advantages—such as accessibility, collaboration, and innovation—and its challenges, including reduced interpersonal interaction, misinformation, digital addiction, and cybersecurity risks. Drawing on scholarly sources, the paper highlights the importance of digital literacy, responsible technology use, and balanced online-offline engagement as essential competencies for students and educators. The study concludes that fostering media literacy and ethical online behavior in education can enhance learning outcomes while mitigating negative consequences of digital dependence.

Keywords: digital communication, education, media literacy, social media, misinformation, digital well-being, cybersecurity

In today's rapidly developing world, digital technology has transformed nearly every aspect of human life, including the way people communicate, learn, and work. The rise of the digital age has made communication faster, easier, and more global than ever before. Through smartphones, the internet, and social media platforms, people can share information instantly and connect with others across borders. In the field of education, digital communication plays a crucial role in expanding access to information, encouraging collaboration, and supporting innovative teaching and learning methods. However, this technological progress also presents new challenges. The growing dependence on online communication has led to a decline in face-to-face interaction, an increase in misinformation and fake news, and issues such as digital addiction and cybersecurity threats. These problems affect not only individuals' social and emotional well-being but also the quality of education and the reliability of shared information. Therefore, understanding how digital communication influences modern life and education is essential. As scholars such as Castells (1996) and Toffler (1980) note, society's shift toward a networked, information-based world requires new ways of thinking and communicating.

Digital communication has become an essential tool in the modern classroom. Online platforms such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and educational forums allow students and teachers to interact beyond physical boundaries. According to Castells (1996), we now live in a "network society," where information flows globally through digital connections. This shift has made education more flexible, interactive, and accessible. Students can attend virtual classes, share ideas instantly, and access digital libraries and open courses. Digital tools also promote inclusivity by allowing students from different locations and backgrounds to collaborate and learn together. However, this reliance on digital communication changes the dynamics of teacher-student relationships. Traditional classroom discussions are often replaced by text-based chats or video calls, which may limit emotional engagement and non-verbal communication cues.

One major drawback of digital communication is the reduction in direct interpersonal contact. Students who primarily communicate online may struggle to express emotions or develop empathy in real-life interactions (Turkle, 2015). Over-reliance on technology can lead to weaker social skills and feelings of isolation. Educational institutions should therefore encourage more in-person collaboration through group projects, debates, and classroom

discussions to balance digital interaction with real-world communication and promote emotional intelligence among learners. The internet provides rapid access to information, but not all online content is accurate. Misinformation and fake news can mislead students and distort their understanding of reality (UNESCO, 2011). In educational contexts, unverified information threatens academic integrity and critical thinking. To address this issue, integrating media and information literacy (MIL) programs into the curriculum can help students learn how to evaluate sources, verify facts, and think critically before sharing information (Hobbs, 2017). Another major challenge of digital communication is digital addiction. Excessive use of social media and digital devices has become a widespread issue among young people. Digital addiction can reduce concentration, increase anxiety, and negatively affect academic performance (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). Students may spend hours scrolling through social networks instead of studying, leading to procrastination and mental fatigue. Educators should teach students about “digital hygiene,” including setting screen time limits, practicing mindfulness, and balancing online activities with offline hobbies like reading, sports, or volunteering. As educational institutions increasingly depend on digital systems, cybersecurity and privacy have become critical concerns. Cyberattacks, data breaches, and identity theft threaten both students and schools (Livingstone & Bulger, 2014).

Many users unknowingly share personal data online without realizing the risks. To counter these threats, schools should implement cybersecurity education programs that teach students how to protect their personal data through strong passwords, two-factor authentication, and secure browsing practices. Governments and organizations also need to enforce stronger data protection laws to safeguard educational institutions and learners. Despite these challenges, digital communication offers tremendous educational benefits. It enhances access to resources, fosters collaborative learning, and supports creativity and innovation. Teachers can use digital tools to make lessons more engaging, interactive, and adaptable to students’ needs. Toffler (1980) emphasized that technological progress, when used responsibly, can empower societies, while Karimov (2008) highlighted that intellectual and moral strength (“ma’naviyat”) must guide modernization. Therefore, developing digital ethics alongside technical skills is vital for future educators and learners. The digital age has revolutionized communication in education, bringing both immense opportunities and serious challenges. While it promotes accessibility, collaboration, and innovation, it can also lead to social disconnection, misinformation, digital addiction, and privacy risks. To address these issues, educational systems must prioritize digital literacy, ethical technology use, and balanced lifestyles. By fostering critical thinking, empathy, and responsibility in the digital environment, schools and universities can prepare students not only to communicate effectively but also to contribute positively to the global information society.

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RAQAMLASHTIRISH DAVRIDA TA'LIMGGA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamlashtirish sharoitida ta'lim tizimida yuz berayotgan tub o'zgarishlar, innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar va zamonaviy tendensiyalar tahlil etiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning o'quv jarayoniga integratsiyalashuvi natijasida vujudga kelayotgan yangi ta'lim modellari, masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlari, sun'iy intellekt va "katta ma'lumotlar" asosida o'qitishni individuallashtirish mexanizmlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, o'qituvchi va o'quvchining raqamli kompetensiyalari muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Raqamlashtirish, innovatsion yondashuvlar, masofaviy ta'lim, gibridd ta'lim, sun'iy intellekt, individuallashtirish, raqamli kompetensiya, STEM, MOOC.*

Annotation: This article analyzes the profound changes taking place in the education system under the conditions of digitalization, as well as innovative pedagogical approaches and modern trends. It highlights new educational models emerging as a result of the integration of digital technologies into the learning process, the opportunities of distance education, and the mechanisms of individualizing instruction based on artificial intelligence and Big Data. The article also discusses the digital competencies of teachers and students.

Keywords: *Digitalization, innovative approaches, distance education, hybrid learning, artificial intelligence, individualization, digital competence, STEM, MOOC.*

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются глубокие изменения, происходящие в системе образования в условиях цифровизации, а также инновационные педагогические подходы и современные тенденции. Освещаются новые образовательные модели, возникающие в результате интеграции цифровых технологий в учебный процесс, возможности дистанционного обучения и механизмы индивидуализации обучения на основе искусственного интеллекта и «Больших данных» (Big Data). Также обсуждаются цифровые компетенции преподавателя и учащегося.

Ключевые слова: *Цифровизация, инновационные подходы, дистанционное обучение, гибридное обучение, искусственный интеллект, индивидуализация, цифровая компетенция, STEM, MOOC.*

XXI asr global taraqqiyotning yangi bosqichini belgilab beruvchi raqamlashtirish jarayoni bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lib, bu jarayon iqtisodiyot, boshqaruv va, ayniqsa, ta'lim sohalarida ulkan transformatsiyalarni keltirib chiqardi. An'anaviy ta'lim paradigmalari zamon talablariga javob bera olmay qolgan bir paytda, raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan innovatsion yondashuvlar ta'lim sifatini oshirish va uning ommabopligini ta'minlashning muhim omiliga aylandi.

Raqamlashtirish ta'lim tizimini asosan uch yo'nalishda o'zgartirmoqda: o'qitish metodologiyasi, ta'lim mazmuni va ta'limni boshqarish jarayonlari. Innovatsion yondashuvlarning asosiy maqsadi o'quvchilarga nafaqat bilim berish, balki ularni raqamli davr talab qiladigan ijodiy fikrlash, muammolarni yechish va hamkorlik qilish ko'nikmalari bilan qurollantirishdir.

Ta'limdagi eng asosiy zamonaviy tendensiyalardan biri gibridd (aralash) ta'lim modelining keng qo'llanilishidir. Gibridd ta'lim an'anaviy yuzma-yuz darslar bilan onlayn

o'qitish elementlarini uyg'unlashtirib, o'quv jarayonini yanada moslashuvchan qiladi. Bu model o'quvchiga o'z tempi va uslubida o'rganish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, pandemiyadan keyingi davrda masofaviy ta'limning yangi platformalar va uslublar bilan takomillashuvi kuzatilmoqda, bu esa geografik to'siqlarni bartaraf etish imkonini beradi [1, 123-b.].

Hozirgi kunda ta'lim jarayoniga sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalarining kirib kelishi katta e'tiborni tortmoqda. SI o'qituvchilarga juda katta yordam bera oladi. Masalan, u o'quvchilarning test natijalari, vazifalarni bajarish tezligi va boshqa ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilib, har bir o'quvchi uchun individuallashtirilgan o'quv traektoriyasini yaratishga qodir. Bu jarayon "Katta ma'lumotlar" (Big Data) tahlili orqali amalga oshiriladi va o'quvchining zaif hamda kuchli tomonlarini aniq ko'rsatib beradi. Natijada, o'qituvchi vaqtini umumiy tushuntirishlarga emas, balki aniq bir o'quvchining muammolarini hal qilishga qaratishi mumkin [2, 354-b.].

Shu bilan birga, ta'lim mazmunida STEM (Fan, Texnologiya, Injeneriya va Matematika) yondashuvining ustuvorligi kuchaymoqda. STEM fanlararo aloqalarni mustahkamlab, nazariy bilimlarni amaliy ko'nikmalar bilan bog'lashga xizmat qiladi. Raqamli muhitda bu yondashuv virtual laboratoriyalar, robototexnika to'garaklari va simulyatsion dasturlar orqali amalga oshirilmoqda.

Global ta'lim tendensiyalaridan yana biri bu ochiq onlayn ommaviy kurslar (MOOCs)ning rivojlanishidir. Coursera, EdX kabi platformalar jahonning yetakchi universitetlari kurslarini hamma uchun ochiq qilib, doimiy o'rganish (lifelong learning) tamoyilini hayotga tatbiq etmoqda.

Raqamli o'zgarishlar sharoitida o'qituvchining roli ham o'zgarib, u bilimlarni oddiy yetkazuvchidan fasilitator (yo'naltiruvchi) va mentorga aylanmoqda. O'qituvchilardan o'quv jarayonida raqamli vositalardan samarali foydalanish, onlayn xavfsizlikni ta'minlash va virtual jamoalarni boshqarish bo'yicha yuqori darajadagi raqamli kompetensiyalar talab etiladi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, raqamlashtirish davrida ta'limga innovatsion yondashuvlarning joriy etilishi muqarrar va zaruriy jarayondir. Gibrid modellar, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan individuallashtirish, STEM yondashuvi va MOOC kabi global tendensiyalar ta'limning sifatini oshirish, uni yanada inklyuziv (qamrab oluvchi) va samarali qilish uchun katta imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Ushbu imkoniyatlardan to'liq foydalanish uchun ta'lim muassasalari, o'qituvchilar va siyosatchilardan o'zgarishlarga tayyor turish va raqamli transformatsiyani strategik boshqarish talab etiladi.

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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND MODERN TRENDS IN EDUCATION IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION

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Annotation: This article explores how digitalization is reshaping the field of education and what innovative methods are being adopted to improve the learning process. It discusses the role of technology in enhancing access to education, encouraging creativity, and supporting more flexible and individualized learning. The study focuses on current trends such as online learning, blended and flipped classroom models, and gamified education. It also touches upon the main challenges faced in implementing digital education, including technological barriers and the need for teachers to develop digital competence.

Keywords: *digitalization, innovation, educational technology, online learning, blended learning, digital competence, interactive methods, creative thinking, modern education.*

Over the past few years, the world has entered an era where technology plays a crucial role in every sphere of life, and education is no exception. The traditional image of a classroom - where a teacher lectures and students listen - is gradually giving way to more dynamic, interactive, and student-centered learning environments. This transformation has largely been driven by digitalization. Digitalization in education does not simply mean using computers or online tools. It represents a deeper change in how knowledge is created, shared, and applied. Teachers today are expected to be facilitators of learning rather than just transmitters of information. Students, on the other hand, have more freedom and responsibility to manage their learning through digital resources and collaboration.

In Uzbekistan, digital transformation in education has become an important part of state policy. Initiatives such as the development of online platforms, digital textbooks, and teacher training programs aim to make learning more efficient and accessible. This creates opportunities for teachers and students to work in a connected environment that promotes innovation and lifelong learning.

The Impact of Digitalization on Education. Digitalization has influenced nearly every aspect of the education system. One of the most significant effects is the expansion of learning opportunities. With platforms like Moodle, Google Classroom, and Coursera, students can access lectures, assignments, and materials anytime and anywhere. This flexibility allows learners to study at their own pace and balance their academic, personal, and professional lives more effectively. Another key benefit is the personalization of learning. Artificial intelligence and data analysis help teachers track student performance and adapt lessons accordingly. These tools can identify learning gaps, suggest additional resources, and provide targeted feedback. As a result, education becomes more responsive to individual needs, helping students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, the introduction of digital tools also requires significant adaptation from both teachers and students. Teachers need to update their methods and gain digital literacy, while students must learn how to use technology responsibly and efficiently. When these two sides align, digital education can lead to better outcomes and more meaningful learning experiences.

Innovative Approaches in Modern Education. Innovation has become the cornerstone of today's teaching and learning processes. Traditional lectures alone are no longer enough to engage students or prepare them for a rapidly changing world. Modern pedagogy now embraces creativity, collaboration, and active participation. Among the most effective methods are gamification, blended learning, and the flipped classroom model. Gamification incorporates elements of play, such as points, rewards, or challenges, into lessons. This approach increases motivation and helps students view learning as an enjoyable and goal-oriented process. Blended learning combines face-to-face interaction with online components,

offering flexibility while maintaining personal contact. The flipped classroom model reverses traditional roles: students first study new material independently at home through videos or readings, then use class time for discussion and practical exercises. This helps develop communication skills, teamwork, and deeper understanding of the material. These innovative methods make lessons more engaging and meaningful. They shift the focus from memorizing facts to developing competencies like creativity, communication, and digital fluency.

Current Trends and Developments. Education around the world is constantly adapting to new technologies. One major trend is the growing importance of digital competence. Being digitally competent now means more than knowing how to use a computer - it includes the ability to analyze information critically, create digital content, and apply ethical principles in online communication. In Uzbekistan, projects such as the Digital Education National Platform and Bilimlar Buluti (Knowledge Cloud) have been introduced to make learning materials widely accessible. These initiatives aim to bridge the digital divide between urban and rural schools and ensure equal access to quality education. Another trend is the use of artificial intelligence in assessment and management systems. AI can help teachers design fairer tests, analyze student progress, and create adaptive learning experiences. This data-driven approach improves teaching efficiency and allows institutions to make informed decisions about curriculum development.

Challenges and Limitations. Despite its many benefits, digitalization also presents several challenges. The most common problem is unequal access to technology. Not all schools have reliable internet connections or sufficient digital resources. This creates a gap between students who can fully benefit from online learning and those who cannot. Another issue is the preparedness of teachers. Some educators may still lack confidence or training in using digital tools effectively. Without proper guidance, technology might be used superficially rather than as a meaningful educational tool. There are also psychological and social concerns. Spending too much time on screens can cause fatigue, reduce attention span, and limit face-to-face communication. Therefore, balancing digital and traditional methods remains essential. Regular teacher training, institutional support, and infrastructure improvement are necessary to overcome these challenges.

Future Perspectives and Recommendations. For digital education to reach its full potential, several steps should be taken. Teachers need continuous training to enhance their digital literacy and pedagogical skills. Educational platforms should be adapted to local needs and languages to ensure inclusivity. Collaboration between schools, universities, and technology companies can help develop new tools and resources. Students should be encouraged to take part in digital projects that promote creativity and independent learning. Ultimately, digitalization should not replace traditional education but complement it. Technology can make education more engaging and flexible, but it must be guided by strong teaching values and human interaction. The goal is to create a learning environment that combines the best of both worlds - technology and pedagogy - to prepare students for the demands of the modern world.

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ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ МОДЕЛИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена анализу современного состояния и перспектив развития цифровых и инновационных технологий в образовании. Рассматриваются основные направления цифровизации учебного процесса, методы и модели их внедрения, а также ключевые проблемы и пути их решения. Особое внимание уделено интеграции технологий искусственного интеллекта, дополненной реальности и адаптивного обучения, а также вопросам цифровой компетентности педагогов и цифровой трансформации образовательных организаций.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация образования, инновационные технологии, искусственный интеллект, адаптивное обучение, цифровая компетентность, образовательные технологии, трансформация.

Abstract: The article analyzes the current state and development prospects of digital and innovative technologies in education. It examines the main directions of digitalization of the learning process, methods and models of their implementation, as well as key challenges and possible solutions. Special attention is given to the integration of artificial intelligence technologies, augmented reality, and adaptive learning, along with issues related to teachers' digital competence and the digital transformation of educational institutions.

Keywords: digitalization of education, innovative technologies, artificial intelligence, adaptive learning, digital competence, educational technologies, transformation.

В современном мире информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ) становятся неотъемлемой частью различных сфер жизни, включая образование. Переход к цифровому обществу требует трансформации традиционных образовательных моделей в более гибкие и инновационные, что предполагает активное внедрение цифровых технологий в учебный процесс. Согласно данным ЮНЕСКО,

цифровизация способствует расширению доступа к знаниям, персонализации обучения и развитию критического мышления у обучающихся.

Цель статьи – выявить перспективы развития и представить практические модели внедрения цифровых и инновационных технологий в образовательный процесс, а также обозначить ключевые проблемы и пути их решения.

В условиях стремительного развития информационно-коммуникационных технологий образование всё чаще становится пространством, где цифровые инновации играют решающую роль. Переход к цифровому обществу требует не просто внедрения новых инструментов, а глубокого пересмотра подходов к обучению, содержания образовательных программ и самой структуры учебного процесса. Согласно международным исследованиям, интеграция цифровых решений способствует расширению доступа к знаниям, персонализации обучения, а также развитию критического мышления и самостоятельности у обучающихся. Всё это обуславливает необходимость переосмысления традиционных моделей образования и поиска эффективных путей внедрения современных технологий в практику.

Одним из наиболее заметных направлений трансформации является развитие дистанционных и гибридных форм обучения. Опыт последних лет показал, что дистанционные технологии позволяют обеспечить доступ к образовательным ресурсам широкому кругу обучающихся. В то же время они выявили ряд организационных и технических проблем, требующих системного решения. Гибридные форматы, сочетающие преимущества очного и дистанционного обучения, стали логичным ответом на вызовы времени, предлагая более гибкий и адаптивный подход к организации учебного процесса.

Значительное внимание уделяется внедрению технологий искусственного интеллекта и адаптивного обучения, позволяющих учитывать индивидуальные особенности обучающихся. Такие системы анализируют данные об успеваемости и предлагают персонализированные траектории обучения, что способствует росту мотивации и повышению эффективности образовательного взаимодействия.

Параллельно развиваются решения на базе дополненной и виртуальной реальности, способствующие формированию интерактивных, иммерсивных образовательных сред. Эти технологии особенно актуальны в сфере технического и медицинского образования, где важна практическая отработка навыков и глубокое понимание сложных понятий. Они позволяют воспроизводить учебные ситуации, которые в традиционной среде реализовать затруднительно.

Немаловажным элементом цифровой трансформации становится использование образовательной аналитики. Сбор и анализ больших массивов данных об обучении позволяют своевременно выявлять проблемные зоны, оптимизировать методики преподавания и принимать обоснованные педагогические решения. Такой подход становится основой для формирования действительно эффективной и гибкой образовательной среды. В зависимости от степени интеграции технологий и готовности образовательной организации можно выделить несколько подходов к цифровой трансформации.

В ряде случаев цифровые инструменты используются как дополнение к традиционному процессу обучения – речь идёт об электронных учебниках, мультимедийных материалах, интерактивных досках и презентациях. Эти элементы улучшают визуальное и практическое восприятие информации, но не изменяют структуру образовательного процесса в целом.

Более продвинутым вариантом является внедрение гибридных моделей обучения, где сочетаются очные занятия и онлайн-элементы. Такие подходы позволяют учитывать особенности разных категорий обучающихся и обеспечивать непрерывность образовательного процесса вне зависимости от внешних обстоятельств.

Наиболее глубокой формой цифровой трансформации можно считать создание полностью виртуальной образовательной среды, в которой все компоненты учебного процесса – от лекций до практических заданий – реализуются через цифровые платформы и специализированные сервисы. Такая модель требует высокого уровня цифровой зрелости образовательной организации, но при этом открывает широкие возможности для индивидуализации и повышения качества образования.

Несмотря на очевидные преимущества цифровизации, её внедрение сопровождается рядом сложностей. Во многих образовательных учреждениях по-прежнему ощущается дефицит технической инфраструктуры и нестабильное интернет-соединение, что ограничивает доступ к современным технологиям. Наряду с этим остаётся актуальной проблема недостаточной цифровой компетентности педагогов. Отсутствие необходимых знаний и навыков в области ИКТ значительно снижает эффективность использования даже самых современных решений.

Для успешной реализации цифровых инициатив в образовании необходимо создание комплексной стратегии, включающей профессиональную подготовку и повышение квалификации педагогов, модернизацию инфраструктуры, разработку методических рекомендаций и создание стандартов этичного и безопасного использования цифровых данных. Только при наличии целостного подхода можно обеспечить устойчивое развитие цифровой образовательной среды и её соответствие современным требованиям.

В итоге рассмотрения данного вопроса можно сказать, что цифровые и инновационные технологии имеют потенциал радикально преобразовать современное образование, сделав его более гибким, доступным и эффективным. Однако успешная реализация этих возможностей требует системного подхода, включающего техническое обеспечение, методическую поддержку, развитие профессиональных компетенций и формирование культуры цифрового взаимодействия. Будущее образования неразрывно связано с постоянным обновлением технологий, пересмотром образовательных практик и готовностью к изменениям всех участников образовательного процесса.

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ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ЦИФРОВЫЕ ПЛАТФОРМЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена анализу инновационных технологий и цифровых платформ, применяемых в обучении русскому языку как иностранному (РКИ). Рассматриваются современные инструменты, их преимущества, ограничения и перспективы развития. Особое внимание уделяется адаптивным системам, мультимедийным материалам, геймификации, виртуальной реальности и использованию искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова: цифровые платформы, видеоуроки, адаптивное обучение, геймификация, виртуальная реальность, искусственный интеллект, смешанное обучение.

Abstract: The article analyzes innovative technologies and digital platforms used in teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL). It examines modern tools, their advantages, limitations, and development prospects. Special attention is given to adaptive learning systems, multimedia materials, gamification, virtual reality, and the use of artificial intelligence in the educational process.

Keywords: digital platforms, video lessons, adaptive learning, gamification, virtual reality, artificial intelligence, blended learning.

Современное образование проходит глубокую трансформацию, связанную с внедрением цифровых технологий и изменениями в методах преподавания. Обучение русскому языку как иностранному обогащается новыми инструментами и подходами, которые не просто дополняют традиционные методы, а создают совершенно новые возможности. Цифровизация обеспечивает адаптивность, мультимедийность и интерактивность, а также расширяет доступ к учебным материалам [2, с. 45].

Централизованные образовательные платформы позволяют организовать обучение с возможностью отслеживания прогресса и поддержки смешанного формата занятий, когда часть учебного процесса происходит онлайн, а часть – офлайн [1, с. 112]. Благодаря адаптивным системам обучение становится персонализированным: уровень и темп занятий подстраиваются под потребности конкретного студента. Технологии Learning Analytics помогают анализировать успеваемость и поведение обучающихся, что повышает эффективность образовательного процесса. Использование мультимедийных материалов, таких как видео, аудио, визуальные иллюстрации и интерактивные упражнения, способствует более глубокому пониманию особенностей произношения, грамматики и лексики.

Геймификация, то есть внедрение игровых элементов, таких как викторины, уровни и награды, делает процесс обучения более мотивирующим и вовлекающим [3, с. 271]. Формат смешанного обучения позволяет сочетать самостоятельную работу с групповыми занятиями, что особенно полезно при ограниченных ресурсах или

географической удалённости обучающихся. Виртуальная и дополненная реальность создают эффект погружения в языковую среду, что способствует развитию навыков, трудно достигаемых традиционными способами. Использование чат-ботов и искусственного интеллекта обеспечивает индивидуальную обратную связь, помогает в автоматической корректировке ошибок и создании адаптивных упражнений, снижая нагрузку на преподавателя.

Онлайн-коммуникация и языковой обмен через цифровые платформы способствуют развитию разговорных навыков и культурной компетенции, создавая условия для аутентичного общения с носителями языка. Тем не менее, несмотря на все преимущества, цифровые технологии сталкиваются с рядом вызовов. Ограничения технической инфраструктуры, такие как неравномерный доступ к качественному интернету и устаревшее оборудование, ограничивают возможности для полного использования современных инструментов. Не все преподаватели обладают необходимыми цифровыми навыками, что требует организации дополнительного обучения и профессионального развития.

Кроме того, не всегда доступен качественный и методически обоснованный контент, адаптированный под особенности изучающих русский язык как иностранный. Отсутствие единых стандартов и методик приводит к хаотичному внедрению технологий, что снижает их эффективность. Перегрузка информацией и избытие разнообразных ресурсов может вызывать у студентов рассеивание внимания и усталость. Также цифровые инструменты не всегда способны создать настоящий эффект языковой среды, особенно при отсутствии живой практики с носителями языка. Важными остаются вопросы этики и приватности данных, а также равный доступ к технологиям для всех обучающихся.

В перспективе можно ожидать расширения использования искусственного интеллекта и машинного обучения для автоматической оценки устной и письменной речи, создания адаптивных упражнений и аналитики ошибок. Виртуальная и дополненная реальность будут всё активнее использоваться для имитации реальных ситуаций общения и культурных взаимодействий. Форматы микрообучения, представляющие собой короткие и удобные для восприятия занятия, помогут интегрировать изучение языка в плотный график студентов. Гибридные модели, сочетающие онлайн и офлайн обучение, позволят максимально эффективно использовать сильные стороны каждого подхода.

Разработка открытых образовательных ресурсов и стандартизация качества цифрового учебного контента способствует повышению доступности и методической обоснованности образовательного процесса. Важным направлением является интеграция межкультурной и социокультурной компетенции в цифровые технологии, создание материалов, отражающих реальную культуру и межъязыковые взаимодействия.

Из сказанного становится очевидным то, что инновационные технологии и цифровые платформы уже сегодня существенно трансформируют процесс обучения русскому языку как иностранному, делая его более гибким, динамичным и персонализированным. Несмотря на существующие трудности, грамотное использование этих технологий позволяет сместить акцент с пассивного запоминания на активную коммуникативную деятельность, повысить мотивацию студентов и адаптировать процесс под их индивидуальные потребности. Ключевыми остаются методическая подготовка преподавателей, качественный контент и надёжная

технологическая инфраструктура, чтобы цифровые инструменты служили именно образовательным целям, а не становились самоцелью.

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ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ МЕДИЙНОЙ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается медийная и информационная грамотность студента как неотъемлемая составляющая профессиональной подготовки. Обосновывается необходимость применения междисциплинарного подхода в формировании медийной и информационной грамотности, предполагающих осознанный подход специалиста к использованию информационно-коммуникационных технологий в профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: медийная и информационная грамотность, профессиональная деятельность, педагог, информационно коммуникационные технологии, информационное общество.

Abstract: The article examines media and information literacy of students as an integral component of professional training. It substantiates the necessity of applying an interdisciplinary approach to the formation of media and information literacy, which involves a conscious and responsible attitude of specialists toward the use of information and communication technologies in their professional activities.

Keywords: media and information literacy, professional activity, educator, information and communication technologies, information society.

Без информационной грамотности очень сложно находиться в современном мире информационных технологий. В XXI веке человек находится в ситуации постоянно нарастающего темпа и ритма жизнедеятельности, при которых он практически постоянно вынужден осваивать новые способы деятельности, основанные на современных технологиях информационного общества. Жизнедеятельность и взаимодействие с другими людьми и миром в целом осуществляется человеком XXI века интегративно в двух социализирующих средах: классической объективной реальности (материально - предметной действительности) и параллельно - альтернативной реальности киберпространства (символьно - знаковой действительности), обе из которых и потенциально и фактически влияют на становление и трансформацию субъективной (явления психики) реальности и действительности. Сегодня киберпространство - сетевое информационное воплощение ноосферы - обретает приоритетные позиции для жизнедеятельности человека, удовлетворения его многочисленных современных потребностей, став средой поиска новых возможностей реализации и трансформации классических видов деятельности: общения в киберкоммуникацию в Сети, игры в досуг в Сети, учения в познание в Сети и труда в работу в Сети. В итоге современный человек - представитель вида «Номо

Sapiens» - становится ещё и «Homo Cyberus'om» - «человеком киберсоциализирующимся». Современные люди разных возрастов ежедневно сталкиваются с необходимостью использования различных гаджетов, производят с ними разнообразные действия, получая и обрабатывая с их помощью гигантские объемы информации. Жизнь в XXI в. ставит человека в относительно жесткие условия, в которых он практически постоянно вынужден осваивать новые способы деятельности, основанные на современных технологиях. Человек приходит к пониманию того, что удовлетворить часть своих потребностей он может, только освоив навыки операционального владения техникой и технологиями. Эти умения позволят ему совершенствоваться и успешно функционировать в социуме, обеспечат комфортную, безопасную, активную жизнедеятельность, будут способствовать его личностному, карьерному росту и благосостоянию. Киберсоциализация личности как неотъемлемый признак современности затрагивает все слои общества, людей разных возрастов, социальных положений и статусов.

Медийно-информационная грамотность (МИГ) - это совокупность знаний, установок, умений и навыков, позволяющих получать доступ к информации и знаниям, анализировать, оценивать, использовать, создавать и распространять их с максимальной продуктивностью в соответствии с законодательными и этическими нормами и с соблюдением прав человека. Медиа - и информационно грамотный человек может использовать различные средства, источники и каналы информации в личной, профессиональной и общественной жизнедеятельности. Медийно-информационная грамотность – это совокупность знаний, навыков, установок, компетенций и практик, которые позволяют обеспечить эффективный доступ, анализ, критическую оценку, интерпретацию, использование, создание и распространение информации и медийных продуктов с использованием всех необходимых средств и инструментов на творческой, законной и этичной основе.

Интенсивное развитие информационно-коммуникационных технологий привели к глобальной информатизации общества и трансформационному переходу от индустриального общества к информационному. Высокий уровень развития информационных ресурсов и соответственно достаточно высокая степень пользования информационными услугами предопределили ряд новых требований к специалистам в разных отраслях знаний. Объем информации, который ежедневно сопровождает каждого из нас, не всегда оказывает благоприятное воздействие и в ряде случаев ставит в трудную ситуацию поиска профессионально корректного решения. Вопрос о том, каков на самом деле характер взаимодействия информации и общества, и всегда ли получаемая информация полезна и способствует правильному разрешению той или иной ситуации, находится под контролем ЮНЕСКО. А.В. Хан, заместитель Генерального директора ЮНЕСКО по вопросам коммуникации и информации, отмечает, что «возрастающие информационные потоки сами по себе являются недостаточным условием для того, чтобы понять те благоприятные возможности для развития, которое дает знание» [4, с. 4]. Современное высшее образование ориентировано на подготовку будущих специалистов, способных к выполнению задач в той или иной профессиональной сфере. Однако сформированный за годы университетского обучения профессиональный навык является не единственным критерием успешности специалиста.

Приступая к обучению в университете, студент не только получает объем специальной информации по конкретному направлению подготовки, но и оказывается в новой для себя социальной среде, формирующей его как личность и будущего

специалиста. Сегодня трудно параметризовать информационное воздействие этой среды, но следует признать масштабы ее манипулятивных возможностей.

Если информационная грамотность «подчеркивает важность доступа к информации, ее оценки и этичного использования», то медийная грамотность «делает акцент на способности понимать функции медиа, оценивать качество выполнения этих функций и вступать в рациональное взаимодействие с медиа в интересах самовыражения» [3, с. 20]. Формирование медийной и информационной грамотности связано, прежде всего, с необходимостью осознания структурообразующей роли меди и информационных каналов в жизни общества. Учитывая масштабы информационного воздействия, можно предположить, что вопрос о формировании информационной грамотности и ее источниках является особенно актуальным. Информационная грамотность проявляет себя в умении критично воспринимать предлагаемые информационные продукты и рационально использовать их для своих образовательных целей. Вопрос о формировании информационной грамотности все чаще рассматривается в академической среде в контексте развития у обучающихся как общекультурных, профессиональных компетенций, так и информационной компетентности. Как отмечают, Н.В. Горбунова и Е.В. Везетиу, формирование информационной компетентности у будущих педагогов возможно в результате «применения в учебно-воспитательном процессе элементов медиа образовательных технологий» и должно осуществляться «с учетом принципа личностного подхода» [2, с. 68]. Сегодня информационная грамотность является одним из показателей уровня развития информационного общества. В связи с переходом общества на новый этап социально-экономического развития изменились требования к подготовке специалиста. В условиях информационного общества не приходится говорить о сформированности тех или иных умений в их окончательном варианте, поскольку специалисту для сохранения высокого квалификационного уровня необходимо постоянное совершенствование уже имеющихся умений и развитие новых. Сформированность данных компетенций представляется возможной в условиях междисциплинарного подхода к обучению медийной и информационной грамотности. При этом следует помнить о том, что формирование медийной и информационной грамотности не сводимо исключительно к профессиональной ориентации обучающихся, наоборот, речь идет о более широком умении «использовать различные средства, источники и каналы информации в личной, профессиональной и общественной жизнедеятельности в соответствии с законодательными и этическими нормами» [1, с. 192]. Овладение информационной грамотностью предполагает сформированность у обучающихся умения работать с электронными ресурсами с целью поиска, критического осмысления и обработки необходимой информации.

Профессиональная подготовка педагога в информационную эпоху сопряжена с формированием у будущего специалиста не просто элементарных представлений об информационной культуре, а определяется степенью сформированности его умений применять информационно-коммуникационные технологии в своей профессиональной деятельности. Представляется, что информационная грамотность будущего педагога – это результат информационного образования, которое должно стать неотъемлемой составляющей его профессиональной подготовки.

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РАЗВИТИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ CLIL ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ

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Аннотация: Современное образование требует от студентов универсальных навыков, включая высокий уровень коммуникативной компетентности, которая является основой для успешной профессиональной деятельности и межкультурной коммуникации. Одним из эффективных методов, способствующих развитию этих навыков, является использование CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) - подхода, при котором учащиеся изучают содержание учебных дисциплин через иностранный язык. Этот подход находит особое применение в обучении студентов нефилологических направлений, поскольку способствует не только улучшению языковой грамотности, но и углублению знаний в своей профессиональной области. Статья рассматривает концепцию CLIL, её влияние на развитие коммуникативных компетенций у студентов нефилологических направлений и методы эффективного использования этого подхода в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная компетентность, CLIL, нефилологические направления, межкультурная коммуникация, учебный процесс, обучение через язык.

Abstract: Modern education demands from students universal skills, including a high level of communicative competence, which is the foundation for successful professional activity and intercultural communication. One of the effective methods promoting the development of these skills is the use of CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning)-an approach where students learn the content of academic subjects through a foreign language. This approach is particularly relevant for students in non-philological fields, as it not only

enhances language proficiency but also deepens their knowledge in their professional domain. The article examines the concept of CLIL, its impact on the development of communicative competencies among students in non-philological fields, and methods for effectively implementing this approach in the learning process.

Keywords: communicative competence, CLIL, non-philological fields, intercultural communication, learning process, language-based education.

Введение. Коммуникативная компетентность является ключевым компонентом образовательного процесса и важнейшим навыком, необходимым для эффективной профессиональной деятельности в условиях глобализации. Она включает в себя не только знание иностранного языка, но и способность использовать его в различных ситуациях общения. Для студентов нефилологических направлений, обучение которых связано с получением знаний в области инженерии, медицины, экономики и других дисциплин, развитие коммуникативных навыков часто становится сложной задачей. В то же время, в условиях глобализации и международного сотрудничества, владение иностранным языком становится неотъемлемой частью их профессиональной карьеры.

Одним из эффективных способов достижения высоких результатов в обучении иностранным языкам является методика CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), которая предполагает использование иностранного языка для изучения специфических дисциплин. Этот подход активно применяется в странах Европы и других регионах, где студенты обучаются не только языку, но и предметным областям через этот язык. Использование CLIL в образовательном процессе позволяет улучшить не только языковые навыки, но и углубить понимание предметных знаний, что в свою очередь способствует развитию коммуникативной компетентности студентов.

Коммуникативная компетентность - это способность эффективно и адекватно взаимодействовать в различных коммуникативных ситуациях, используя знания и навыки в области языка, культуры и контекста. Важнейшими компонентами коммуникативной компетентности являются: лексическая, грамматическая, дискурсивная, социокультурная и стратегическая компетенции. Уровень развития этих компонентов напрямую зависит от образовательной среды и методов преподавания, а также от специфики обучения иностранным языкам.

CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) представляет собой методику, в которой обучение иностранному языку происходит одновременно с изучением определённого контента - предметных дисциплин. В отличие от традиционного подхода, когда языковое обучение сосредоточено только на языке, CLIL способствует интеграции языкового и предметного компонентов, что делает обучение более эффективным и контекстуально значимым для студентов.[1,5]

Основная цель CLIL - это развитие языковой компетенции через погружение в контекст специализированных дисциплин. В этом контексте важным аспектом становится не просто усвоение языковой структуры, а способность применять язык в реальных профессиональных ситуациях, что в значительной степени способствует развитию коммуникативной компетентности.

Для студентов нефилологических направлений обучение через CLIL имеет особую значимость, так как они, как правило, не являются носителями иностранного языка и имеют ограниченный опыт общения на языке в профессиональном контексте. Введение CLIL в образовательный процесс этих студентов позволяет:

1.Повышение мотивации и интереса: Изучение специализированных предметов на иностранном языке помогает студентам осознать значимость языка как инструмента для расширения их профессиональных горизонтов. Это позволяет

повысить мотивацию к изучению языка, так как студенты видят реальную пользу от овладения языковыми навыками в контексте своей будущей профессии.

2. Развитие межкультурной компетенции: Обучение через CLIL способствует углублению знаний о культуре и профессиональных традициях стран, говорящих на изучаемом языке. Это особенно важно в условиях глобализации, когда межкультурная коммуникация становится неотъемлемой частью профессиональной деятельности.

3. Углубление знаний в предметной области: Студенты получают возможность изучать материал своей специальности на иностранном языке, что способствует лучшему усвоению материала и одновременно развивает языковые навыки.

4. Применение языка в реальных профессиональных ситуациях: CLIL позволяет студентам практиковать язык в реальных контекстах, что способствует формированию устойчивых навыков коммуникации в профессиональной сфере.[4]

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THE FUTURE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN THE AGE OF AI

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Annotation: The article reviews the role of artificial intelligence in English Language Teaching, focusing on tools such as adaptive learning systems, automated assessment platforms, gamified applications, and generative AI. It explains how these technologies enhance personalization, provide immediate feedback, and increase learner engagement. At the same time, the article notes challenges such as ethical issues, potential overreliance on technology, and the need for teacher training. Overall, it presents AI as a major force reshaping the methods and practices of English teaching worldwide.

Key words: globalization, teaching, Artificial Intelligence, education, tool, adaptive learning, platform, human factor, learning affordable, interactive learning.

Introduction. Digital technology is revolutionizing education, with artificial intelligence at the forefront. This transformative AI wave has attracted attention from substantial numbers of educational researchers and practitioners to exploit AI's pedagogical potential. And there is a statement that every person who's related to linguistics faces: "Will AI replace English teachers, or will it become their most powerful assistant?" Since AI has become the most useful source in every aspect of people's life, it also shows rapid growth in the education system. Because of informative recommendations, individual guidance to educators or students, it quickly spread around them. Even some people believe that learning languages by AI is more efficient than taking real life classes. Actually, they have a point, as

the proverb says, “A horse runs faster alone”. When a learner studies with one specific mentor who works individually, adapted to the student's pace, it works well. But remember, AI is a tool. It is transforming English teaching, but it should be seen as a tool that compliments, not replaces human teachers. As mentioned in the continuation of the proverb above, “A horse runs faster alone, but it doesn’t go far”. AI’s current role in language learning. Learning a new language means opening new doors of quests. Familiarizing new cultures, trying new tastes, meeting with strangers and their habits that surprise you gives amazing feelings about lingualism. Maybe therefore most people love to learn languages. Especially, if it’d be Lingua Franca like English. To accomplish this objective, ChatBots(Chat GPT), Duolingo’s AI tutor and adaptive learning platforms help easily. They have got lots of beneficial sides of these platforms. For example, personalized feedback. When you study with a teacher in the classroom, your teacher can not focus on each of the students. Also, instant corrections and 24/7 availability can not be found in teachers sometimes. Additionally, after AI availability, people who want to learn languages but live in remote areas can now access quality language support. We can say that this is the most powerful and useful achievement in our era.

Advantages of AI in ELT. AI technologies bring several advantages that traditional classrooms alone cannot always provide. As an example we can see the personalization: AI adjusts to learners’ pace and needs, ensuring that each student receives targeted practice. And also efficiency: Teachers can rely on AI to handle repetitive tasks such as grammar drills, spelling checks, or quiz grading.

Engagement: Gamified applications make learning more enjoyable, motivating students to practice consistently.

Accessibility: AI platforms are available anytime and anywhere, breaking down geographical and economic barriers to education. There are more and more examples that Artificial intelligence can be used in as the best assistant in learning language system. **Limitations and Concerns** Despite these benefits, the integration of AI into ELT raises important concerns:

The human factor: AI cannot replace empathy, motivation, or cultural awareness provided by teachers.

Overreliance: Excessive dependence on AI tools may weaken learners’ critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Bias and accuracy: AI systems sometimes generate incorrect, biased, or culturally insensitive content.

Teacher adaptation: Many educators feel unprepared to incorporate AI effectively into their teaching, creating gaps in classroom practice.

The Future: Partnership Between AI and Teachers.

The most promising future for ELT lies in a partnership between AI and human educators. Rather than competing with teachers, AI can complement their role. Machines can take care of repetitive exercises and assessments, while teachers focus on creativity, communication, and nurturing learner confidence. To achieve this balance, teacher training programs must include digital literacy and AI integration strategies. In this way, English classrooms of the future will combine technological efficiency with the irreplaceable human touch.

Conclusion. Artificial intelligence is not a passing trend but a powerful force reshaping English Language Teaching. However, it is not a substitute for teachers-it is a tool that, when used wisely, can enrich the learning process. The challenge for educators, policymakers, and students alike is to embrace AI responsibly, ensuring that it enhances rather than diminishes the human essence of education. The classrooms of tomorrow will belong not to machines or

humans alone, but to both, working together to create more effective and inclusive language learning experiences.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF WIKI TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article explores how wiki technology serves as an effective tool for developing and enhancing writing skills in educational and professional contexts. It examines the collaborative nature of wikis, their role in facilitating peer feedback, building critical thinking abilities, and fostering confidence through iterative writing processes. The article discusses practical applications across various settings while acknowledging potential challenges in implementation.

Keywords: wiki technology, collaborative writing, writing skills development, peer feedback, digital literacy, educational technology, knowledge management, iterative writing process, online collaboration, writing instruction

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается, как вики-технология служит эффективным инструментом для развития и совершенствования навыков письма в образовательном и профессиональном контексте. В статье рассматривается коллективная природа вики-технологий, их роль в обеспечении обратной связи от коллег, развитии критического мышления и укреплении уверенности в себе посредством итеративного процесса письма. В статье рассматриваются практические применения в различных условиях, а также отмечаются потенциальные сложности при внедрении.

Ключевые слова: вики-технология, совместное письмо, развитие навыков письма, обратная связь от коллег, цифровая грамотность, образовательные технологии, управление знаниями, итеративный процесс письма, онлайн-сотрудничество, обучение письму

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola viki-texnologiyasi ta'lim va professional kontekstlarda yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish va yaxshilash uchun samarali vosita sifatida qanday xizmat qilishini o'rganadi. Vikilarning hamkorlikdagi tabiati, tengdoshlar fikr-mulohazalarini osonlashtirish, tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish va takrorlanuvchi yozish jarayonlari orqali ishonchni mustahkamlashdagi rolini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqola joriy etishdagi potensial qiynchiliklarni tan olgan holda turli sharoitlarda amaliy qo'llanilishini muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: viki-texnologiya, hamkorlikda yozish, yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, tengdoshlar fikr-mulohazasi, raqamli savodxonlik, ta'lim texnologiyasi, bilimlarni boshqarish, takrorlanuvchi yozish jarayoni, onlayn hamkorlik, yozishni o'rgatish

In an increasingly digital world, developing strong writing skills has never been more crucial. While traditional methods of teaching writing remain valuable, wiki technology has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing writing abilities across educational and professional contexts. This collaborative platform offers unique advantages that can transform how individuals learn, practice, and refine their writing.

Wiki technology refers to collaborative web platforms that allow multiple users to create, edit, and organize content collectively. The most famous example is Wikipedia, but wikis exist in countless forms across educational institutions, businesses, and communities. The defining characteristic of wiki technology is its openness to collaborative editing, version control, and transparent revision history.

One of wiki technology's most significant contributions to writing development is its facilitation of collaborative learning. Unlike traditional writing assignments completed in isolation, wikis enable writers to receive immediate feedback from peers, instructors, or colleagues. This collaborative environment creates several benefits:

Writers can observe how others approach similar topics, learning different organizational strategies and writing techniques. The ability to see revision histories allows learners to understand the writing process as iterative rather than linear, demystifying how good writing develops through multiple drafts. Peer review becomes integrated into the writing process rather than a separate, final step, encouraging writers to view their work as part of an ongoing conversation.

Working with wiki technology naturally develops critical thinking and editing abilities. When writers know their work will be publicly visible and potentially edited by others, they become more thoughtful about clarity, accuracy, and evidence. This accountability encourages more careful research and more precise language.

Additionally, contributing to wikis often involves editing others' work, which builds essential editorial skills. By identifying weaknesses in others' writing, individuals become better at recognizing similar issues in their own work. This meta-cognitive awareness is fundamental to becoming a stronger writer.

Building Confidence Through Incremental Progress

Wiki technology's revision control system preserves every change, creating a visible record of improvement over time. Writers can look back at earlier versions of their work and see tangible evidence of their progress. This documentation of growth builds confidence and motivation, helping writers recognize that improvement comes through sustained effort rather than innate talent alone.

The low-stakes nature of wiki contributions also reduces the anxiety often associated with writing. Because work can be continuously revised and improved, writers feel less pressure to produce perfect first drafts. This environment encourages experimentation and risk-taking, both essential for developing an authentic writing voice.

The skills developed through wiki technology translate across various writing contexts. In educational settings, wikis can support collaborative research projects, shared note-taking, and group presentations. Students learn to synthesize information from multiple sources, credit contributors appropriately, and write for specific audiences.

In professional environments, wikis serve as knowledge management systems, project documentation platforms, and training resources. Employees who contribute to these systems develop technical writing skills, learn to communicate complex information clearly, and practice writing for diverse stakeholders.

Despite its benefits, wiki technology also presents challenges. The open editing model can sometimes lead to conflicts over content, requiring users to develop negotiation and

communication skills alongside writing abilities. Ensuring accuracy and preventing vandalism requires active moderation and clear guidelines.

Additionally, the informal nature of some wikis may not always encourage formal writing skills. Educators and administrators must provide clear expectations and models to ensure wiki projects develop the desired writing competencies.

Wiki technology represents a valuable tool for improving writing skills in the 21st century. By fostering collaboration, providing immediate feedback, documenting progress, and creating authentic writing contexts, wikis address many limitations of traditional writing instruction. As digital literacy becomes increasingly essential, integrating wiki technology into writing education prepares individuals not only to write well but to participate effectively in the collaborative, knowledge-building activities that define modern work and learning.

The key to maximizing wiki technology's potential lies in thoughtful implementation. When supported by clear learning objectives, appropriate scaffolding, and meaningful feedback, wikis can transform writing from a solitary, intimidating task into an engaging, collaborative process of continuous improvement.

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THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya. Bu kunlarda zamonaviy texnologiyalar bizning hayotimizda, ayniqsa ta'limda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada til o'rganishda innovatsion texnologiyalarning ahamiyati, o'quvchilarning yangi tilni o'rganishga qiziqishini qanday oshirish mumkinligi, samarali usullarni qo'llash, darslarda texnologiyalarning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, ta'lim, xorijiy til, zamonaviy, innovatsion.

Аннотация. В наши дни современные технологии играют важную роль в нашей жизни, особенно в образовании. В этой статье будет обсуждено значение инновационных технологий в изучении языков, как учащиеся могут заинтересоваться изучением нового языка с помощью современных технологий, использование эффективных методов, а также преимущества и недостатки технологий на уроках.

Ключевые слова: технология, образование, иностранный язык, современный, инновационный.

Abstract. These days, modern technologies have a crucial role in our life, especially in education. In this article the important of innovative technologies in language learning, how learners can be interested in studying a new language though modern technologies, the use of effective methods, advantages and disadvantages of technologies during lessons will be discussed.

Key words: technology, education, foreign language, modern, innovative.

Nowadays, the interest in using interactive methods, innovative technologies and pedagogical technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. Therefore, it is intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies in the process of language learning. As the president of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "In the field of education, we consistently continue to create the most favorable conditions for our children to master modern knowledge and skills." [1] The use of computer technologies in language learning increases students' interest in language. The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be seen that different attitudes were expressed in the use of different technologies in foreign language teaching.

Currently, the desire to learn languages is increasing from day to day, at the same time, people are using various technologies to learn languages faster, more effectively and they are making education interactive and interesting. Noam Chomsky states, the process of learning a language is one of the most complex tasks for human brain. [2] Modern technologies simplify and enhance this process. Besides that, conditions have been created to educate the growing younger generation in a well-rounded manner so they can master modern technologies and skills effectively. We can also consider David Crystal [3] referred, "Modern technologies create new opportunities for language learning. The Internet and mobile applications provide the ability to learn anywhere and at any time. Special attention has also been given to teaching foreign languages within the ongoing reforms. The resolution adopted on December 10, 2012 regarding measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages has played an important role in this regard. Modern technologies provide students with new ways to learn languages. Sir Ken Robinson [5] emphasizes; "It is essential to encourage creativity in the education process. Technologies serve as a powerful tool for this, as they make the educational process interactive and engaging." For example, students can

strengthen their knowledge through mobile applications and videos. Moreover, they can express their attitudes towards information or analyze unclear points, enhancing communication among students. One of the modern technologies is the internet which is the key to the successful development of any nation. One of the most commonly used modern approaches today is the use of multimedia in classrooms. Multimedia includes using video presentations, animations and interactive diagrams to showcase

It is important to mention that technology has both positive and negative aspects in modern language education. For instance, online platforms allow students to communicate with language learners in other countries and they can use various resources, video tutorials and games available on the internet. Also language learning apps enable learners to practice anytime and anywhere features like quizzes, flashcards and games encourage active participation and reinforce vocabulary etc. The downside is that students may often get distracted by other things while using technology and not all online materials and programs are of the same quality which may provide them with incorrect information. In short, this can lead to technology dependence and isolation.

The role of technology in language learning is twofold: on the one hand, it makes learning easier and more effective. On the other hand, if used carelessly, it can have harmful effects. Balancing its positive and negative aspects is crucial. We must also keep in mind our president's words: "Technologies are the strongest tools for connecting with the world."

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ АНТОНИМИИ В КАЧЕСТВЕ ЛЕКСИКО -
СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация. Единицы языка «погружены» в систему языка, образуемую ими, то есть в «множество языковых элементов любого естественного языка, находящихся в отношениях и связях друг с другом, которые образуют определенное единство и целостность» [1. С. 452].

Ключевые слова: система, лексико - семантическое значение, парадигма, антонимы, синонимы, омонимы, паронимы, родо - видовые отношения.

Введение. Любой объект, в том числе язык, можно рассматривать, по крайней мере, в трёх отношениях:

- а) как определённую совокупность элементов;
- б) как определённую совокупность отношений между этими элементами;
- в) как связное целое, то есть как определённую совокупность элементов и отношений, существующую в силу воплощения элементов в определённую субстанцию [2. С. 24].

Обсуждение. По определению В. М. Солнцева, «система есть целостный объект, состоящий из элементов, находящихся во взаимных отношениях» [3. С. 14].

Языковая система представляет собой «систему систем», «иерархически организованную совокупность взаимосвязанных ярусов или уровней» (2. С. 74].

Каждый из этих языковых ярусов, в том числе лексико-семантический, имеет определённое устройство, характеризуясь известной упорядоченностью единиц. «Устройство, организация, упорядоченность системы представляет собой структуру этой системы ... Структуру системы можно иначе определить как совокупность внутрисистемных связей» [3. С. 28-29].

Лексическая система представляет собой самую сложную систему, существования которой долгое время ставилось под сомнение. Первой попыткой системной интерпретации языка явилась концепция лексики, отражённая в «Тезисах» Пражского лингвистического кружка (1920 г.): «Многие лингвисты полагали, что в противоположность морфологии, образующей строгую систему, словарь представляет собой хаос, в котором, пользуясь алфавитом, можно навести только внешний порядок. Это очевидное заблуждение. Правда, лексические системы намного сложнее и шире систем морфологических, так что лингвистом вряд ли удастся когда-либо представить их с такой же ясностью и точностью, как последние; однако если слова действительно противопоставлены друг другу или взаимосвязаны, то они образуют системы, формально аналогичные системам морфологическим, и, следовательно, тоже могут изучаться лингвистами» [4. С. 38].

Обычно отмечают такие особенности лексической системы, как её многомерность, открытость, сложность и гибкость отношения единиц и контекста, что, безусловно, в значительной степени затрудняет её изучение и описание.

Признание самостоятельности слов и объективных условий их противопоставления «даёт возможность исследовать системные отношения, так сказать, и вширь, и вглубь: изучение полисемии позволяет воссоздать систему

значений, систему лексико-семантических вариантов (внутри) одного слова, а анализ взаимоотношений слов друг с другом воссоздаёт (внешние) связи слова, определяющие динамику системы, – синонимические, антонимические, омонимические, паронимические, гипонимические, аллонимические и некоторые другие» [5. С. 5].

Наряду со словом (лексемой) как основной единицей языка, парадигматической целостностью, в структуре лексики исключительную ценность имеет минимальная конструктивная единица – отдельное значение слова, или лексико-семантический вариант (ЛСВ). Само слово представляет собой смысловую структуру таких вариантов, которые «различаются своими лексическими значениями (причём различия между этими значениями не выражается в их звуковых оболочках)» [Смирницкий А. И. Лексикология английского языка. – М., 1954. С. 36].

ЛСВ оказываются теми элементарными единицами, из которых конструируются различные категории лексики и их единицы: полисемия – многозначное слово, синонимия – синонимический ряд, антонимия – антонимическая пара и так далее. Если иметь в виду многозначные слова, то очень часто можно видеть, как такие слова входят в синонимические и антонимические отношения сразу с несколькими словами (ЛСВ). Особый интерес для рассматриваемой в работе проблемы представляет собой взаимосвязь и взаимодействие антонимии и синонимии, те семантические отношения, которые существуют между антонимами и синонимами.

П. Н. Денисов к объединениям, которые обеспечивает системность лексики, относит: «... 1) семантическое поле, 2) лексико-семантическую группу, 3) ситуативную группу, 4) коммуникативную группу, 5) родо-видовую группу (рубрика тезауруса), 6) синонимический ряд, 7) антонимическую пару, 8) словообразовательное гнездо, 9) эпидигматическую группу (совокупность всех значений или ЛСВ многозначного слова)».

Не все приведённые автором предыдущего высказывания объединения являются объединениями лексем: семантическое поле и эпидигматическая группа – это по сути объединение языковых значений, ситуативная и коммуникативная группы – объединение функционального характера, кроме того, к выделенным группам следует добавить тематические группы, энантиосемию, омонимию («отрицательную», но очень важную для системы и функционирования языка парадигматику), паронимию. Ко всем названным объединениям антонимы имеют прямое отношение, однако наиболее существенное и частотные типы пересечений и взаимодействий наблюдаются между антонимами и следующими типами объединений: 1) полисемией; 2) синонимией; 3) родо-видовыми (гиперо-гипонимическими) парадигмами; 4) словообразовательным гнездом; 5) семантическим полем; 6) энантиосемией.

Вопрос о роли, какую играет антонимия как выражение одного из универсальных отношений в системе языка тесно связан таким образом с возможно полным учётом всех системных отношений противоположных по семантике слов, включая сюда и производные слова, отражающие в той или иной степени семантику исходных.

Важнейшим критерием антонимии в целом, независимо от типа и непроизводности/производности слов, является семантический: это отрицание друг друга единицами, однородными по смысловой структуре.

С нашей точки зрения, антонимию, как и другие языковые явления, целесообразно описывать с точки зрения полевой структуры, то есть выделения в ней ядра и периферии. Ядерную часть антонимии в любом языке составляют слова качественные семантики, взаимосвязанные и противоположные по семантике,

манифестирующие крайние, предельные точки качественной шкалы оценки (**хороший – плохой, добрый – злой, добро – зло, друг – враг**), а сложно устроенную периферию составляют слова с противоположными или даже противопоставленными значениями, не всегда отвечающие вышеизложенным строгим критериям. Ведь даже в общепринятой паре глагольных антонимов **любить – ненавидеть** только второй коррелят представляет крайнюю точку качественной оценки отрицательной эмоции, тогда как положительный коррелят (многозначный глагол, отражающий разные виды в степени положительного отношения к объекту) фактически не обозначает «предела оценки», для чего больше подходит глагол **обожать**. Очевидно, поэтому Л. А. Новиков другой своей работе выдвигает в качестве критерия «истинной» антонимии обозначение предела оценки только для одного противочлена антонимической пары. В то же время в разных языках соотношение ядра и периферии антонимии может существенно различаться.

По нашему мнению, важно не столько подвести те или иные парадигмы под строгие логические критерии антонимии, сколько исследовать реальные типы противоположности и противопоставленности в данном языке.

Практически все современные лингвисты согласны с тем, что в основе языковых значений лежат не строгие логические понятия, а скорее обычные, близкие к бытовым, изменчивые, обладающие лишь относительной точностью. «Единая лексическая система языка в современных условиях фактически существует в виде двух связанных друг с другом систем: обыденной (языковой «картины мира») и научной («картины мира»). Многие всеобщие семасиологи и ономазиологи, занимающиеся идеографией и семантическими полями, полагают, что языкознание должно сосредоточить свои усилия на изучение концептуальных схем, на которых покоится исконная, языковая «картина мира», соответствующее уровню обыденного (наивного) сознания житейскому здравому смыслу. Исследование и описание «научных картин мира» – дело энциклопедической, научно-технической и специальной лексикографии».

Антонимические отношения представляют собой самый «сильный» тип парадигматических отношений, «антонимы просто невысказаны друг без друга. Они могут быть поняты только одновременно».

В энциклопедии «Русский язык» представлена содержательная статья «Антонимы» (автор Л. А. Новиков), сочетающая логические, психологические и лингвистические критерии антонимии: «**антонимы** – слова одной и той же части речи, имеющие противоположные значения. Обозначая противоположные проявления одной и той же сущности, антонимы взаимно отрицают и в то же время предполагают друг друга. **Горячий** и **холодный** одновременно обозначают предел проявления качества, свойства, состояния предметов (то есть границы качественной оценки температуры), и указывают на неразрывную связь противоположностей. Психологическую основу антонимии образуют ассоциации представлений по контрасту, логическую – противоположные видовые понятия, например, **чёрный** и **белый** внутри понятия «ахроматический цвет».

Антонимы выражают предельное отрицание противоположного значения, вскрываемого путём семантического анализа: **сильный – слабый** (=предельно не +сильный)».

Примечательно, что для определения антонимии Л. А. Новиковым задействованы не только понятие «противоположность», но и понятие «отрицание», «контраст», «род – вид», а также категория оценки.

Таким образом, все определения антонимов подчёркивают определяющую черту, отличающую данный вид лексической парадигматики от синонимии, гиперо-гипонимических отношений и т. д. – наличие противоположности или противопоставленности в семантике.

Итак, антонимы – семантически однородные слова, соответствующие видовым понятиям одного родового понятия, различающиеся по одному существенному для их содержания дифференциальному признаку. Логически **высокий** и **низкий** – крайние, предельные видовые понятия родового понятия «линейный размер (протяженность) снизу вверх», между которыми возможно промежуточное понятие (средний):

Роль семантического критерия, как будет показано далее, очень существенно при оценке производных слов, так как значение словообразовательных форматов и сам процесс межчастеречной трансформации производных (в другой класс слов) могут приводить к таким их смысловым модификациям, что такие слова перестают быть истинными антонимами в результате различных отклонений в механизмах отражения.

Заключение. В заключение следует обратить внимание на то, что как исходные (непроизводные), так и производные (или словообразовательные) антонимы должны быть словами, выражающими качественные значения, или обозначающими направленные взаимно противоположные действия, качества, свойства, признаки (последнюю противоположность, а также разновидность антонимии иногда называют векторной).

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NEMIS TILIDA FRAZEOLOGIK SINONIMLARNING STRUKTURASI VA SINONIMIK HAMDA VARIANTLIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada nemis tilidagi frazeologik sinonimlarning strukturaviy tuzilishi va sinonimik xususiyatlari va ularni o‘zbek tilida ifodalanishi imkoniyatlari to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritiladi. Maqolada nemis tilidagi strukturaviy frazeologik sinonimlarning kelib chiqish tarixiga ham to‘xtalib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: frazeologiya, frazeologizm, frazeologik sinonim, strukturaviy frazeologizm, so‘z boyligi, xususiyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются структурное строение и синонимические особенности фразеологических синонимов немецкого языка, а также возможности их передачи на узбекском языке. В работе также уделяется внимание истории возникновения структурных фразеологических синонимов в немецком языке.

Ключевые слова: Фразеология, фразеологизм, фразеологический синоним, структурный фразеологизм, богатство слов, особенность.

Abstract: This article discusses the structural composition and synonymic features of phraseological synonyms in the German language, as well as the possibilities of their rendering in Uzbek. The study also touches upon the historical development of structural phraseological synonyms in German.

Keywords: phraseology, idiom, phraseological synonym structural phraseological unit, lexical richness, characteristic.

Frazeologik sinonimiya deganda ma'nodosh va ma'no jihatdan o'xshash frazeologizmlar tushuniladi. Ular paradigmatic darajalar bilan birgalikda farqlovchi xususiyatga ham ega bo'ladi.

Frazeologik sinonimiya nemis frazeologiyasining mahsuldor va muhim kategoriyalaridan biridir. Bu lingvistik maqomga ega barqaror so'z birikmalar guruhiga mansubdir. Uning konotativ ma'nosi bir nechta so'zli tarkibiy qismlardan tashkil topgan bo'lib, doimiy ravishda yangi frazeologizmlarni yuzaga keltiradi va tilning sinonimik qatlamini to'ldirib boradi. Frazeologik sinonimiya leksikdagi kabi xususiyatlarga ega:

A) **ma'nodosh**, masalan: *das Pferd beim Schwanz aufzäumen – den Aal beim Schwanz fassen* „eine Sache verkehrt anfangen“ – ishni teskarisidan (aksidan) boshlamoq; o'z-o'ziga dahmaza orttirmoq.

B) **ideografik** masalan: *einen Affen [sitzen] haben* „betrunken sein“ (маст-аласт бўлмоқ) - *einen (kleinen) Aal haben* „leicht betrunken sein“ (sarmast bo'lmoq).

C) **stilistik**, masalan: *die Augen schließen*, (дунёдан кўз юммоқ), *ins Gras beißen*, salopp, derb „sterben“ (o'lmoq, vafot etmoq, jon bermoq, yer tishlamoq).

D) **ma'lum bir hududga xos**: mintaqaviy, hududiy, masalan: schwäb. *Dear haut nix äs Läus*, und *dia send krank gemeind. arm sein wie eine Kirchenmaus* (bir tiyini ham yo'q, cho'ntagida hemiri ham bo'lmaslik).

Frazeologik sinonimiyaning leksik sinonimiyaga qaragandagi mukammal xususiyati shundaki, undagi ma'nodosh sinonimlar salmoqli miqdorni tashkil qiladi. Ular sintagmatik darajada bir-biriga o'xshash bo'ladi va shuning uchun ham ular mutlaq sinonimlar deb nomlanadi. Shunday ekan, mutlaq sinonimlar deganda ma'no va uslubiy belgilanmaslik nuqtai nazaridan bir xil bo'lgan frazeologizmlar tushuniladi. Shakliy jihatdan ular frazeologik sinonimlarning boshqa barcha turlariga xos xususiyatlarga ega: A) bir xil strukturali frazeologik sinonimlar, masalan: *in die Pilze gehen, in die Nüsse gehen; in die Binsen gehen, in die Wicken gehen* – „verloren gehen, verschwinden“ ertrinken und verderben" – dom daraksiz yo'qolib ketmoq. B) har xil strukturali frazeologik sinonimlar, masalan: *einen Vogel haben, bei dem piept's wohl, nicht alle Tassen im Schrank haben, bei jmdm. spukt es im Kopf* – “nicht recht bei Verstand sein” – aqldan ozgan bo'lmoq. Yoki masalan, *leeres Stroh dreschen. Holz in den Wald tragen, Wasser im Siebe tragen, Wasser mit einem Sieb schöpfen* - „vergebliche, unnütze Arbeit tun“ – bekorchi ish bilan shug'ullanmoq.

Nemis tilida strukturaviy sinonimlar ham mavjud va bunday sinonimlar ko'p miqdorni tashkil etadi. Genetik mezonlarga ko'ra bunday frazeologizmlarning ikki turi mavjud. Ulardan biriga quyidagi frazeologizmlar kiradi: 1. Metaforik o'zgarish natijasida turli xil verbal so'z birikmalaridan tashkil topgan frazeologizmlar masalan, *in die Pilze gehen* (dom daraksiz yo'qolmoq) kabi birikmalar. Leksikografik manbalarga ko'ra ushbu qatorga mansub eng qadimgi sinonimlardan biri bo'lgan *in die Pilze gehen* (XVII asrga mansub) frazeologizmning ma'nosi qo'ziqorin izlovchilarining o'rmonda adashib qolish holati bilan qiyoslash asosida yuzaga kelgan.

XIX asrga mansub frazeologik sinonimlar tahminlarga ko'ra ovchilar tiildan kelib chiqqan, bunga esa itdan qochayotgan yovvoyi o'rdak suvga tushib qutilgan va qamishzor orasiga berkinganligi sabab bo'lgan. Shu bilan ovchilar o'rdaklarni yovvoyi o'tlar orasiga kirib ketgan va ularning chirmashib ketgan poyalar va shoxlar orasidan topib bo'lmaydigan hayvonni yo'qotgandek, uni ham topa olishmaydi. Natijada ushbu qatorda bir-biridan mustaqil va til rivojlanishining turli davrlarida yuzaga kelgan turli xil frazeologizmlar mavjud. Bu turning ikkinchi guruhiga esa frazeologizmlarning bir yoki bir nechta tarkibiy qismlarini almashtirish imkoniyati asosida shakllangan sinonimlar kiradi. Bu turdagi sinonimlar guruhiga quyidagilarni eng ko'p ishlatiladiganlarini misol qilib ko'rsatish mumkin: Masalan: *jmdm. geht ein Licht auf, jmdm. geht ein Seifensieder auf* – „jmd. versteht, durchschaut plötzlich etw“ “ko'zlari moshdek ochilmoq” – biror narsani to'satdan tushunib yetish, anglab olish.

Bunday sinonimik qatlamda hazil ohangni yoki ifoda kuchini oshirish maqsadida bir frazeologik birlikning turlicha ekanini uchratish mumkin. Masalan: *alter Mann (od. alte Oma) ist doch kein D-Zug, alter Mann (od. alte Oma) ist doch kein Düsenjäger* - „ich kann nicht so schnell wie du möchtest“ (men senga o'xshab bunchalik tez yura olmayman).

O'zgaruvchan komponentlarga ega strukturaviy frazeologik sinonimlar ayniqsa, semantik va vazifadosh xususiyatini yaqqol ochib beradi va tilning frazeologik boyligi shu yo'l bilan doimiy ravishda boyib borishiga sabab bo'ladi. “Aqldan ozgan bo'lmoq” kabi frazeologizmni asosiy ma'noga ega bo'lgan sinonimik qator bilan taqqoslagan holda, shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, u zamonaviy tilshunoslikda o'nlab og'zaki uslubdagi sinonimlarni o'z ichiga oladi va doimiy ravishda yangi sinonimlar hamda ularning yangi variantlari bilan boyib boradi. Masalan: *nicht alle Lichter am Baum haben (aqli joyida bo'lmaslik – yoshlarga xos zamonaviy til uslubi)*, *Jugenddeutsch*, und das ältere Synonym *nicht alle auf dem Christbaum haben (aqldan ozgan, telba – eskiroq varianti)*.

“Strukturaviy sinonimlar” atamasi hanuzgacha ilmiy adabiyotlarda munozaralarga sabab bo'lmoqda. Bu kabi birikmalar sinonimmi yoki variantmi shuni aniqlab olish lozim. Fikrimizcha, komponentlari o'rin almasha oladigan frazeologik birikmalar ba'zida sinonim, ba'zida esa variant sifatida baholanadi – bu esa ularni almashtirish ma'noga va funksiyaga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishiga bog'liq. Agar tarkibiy qismlarning o'rin almashtirilishi asosiy birlik bilan solishtirilganda semantik, uslubiy yoki hududiy tafovutni yuzaga keltirsa, bu holatda to'liq asos bilan ularni sinonimlar deb atash mumkin. Shu o'rinda ishonarli qilib kuyidagi misolni, o'rin almashtira oladigan, otli komponentlar uslubiy farqlanishlarni yuzaga keltiradigan frazeologizmlarni keltrish mumkin: *den Mund halten*, ugs (neytral shakli), *den Rand halten*, salopp, derb. (juda qo'pol shakli) - –“schweigen“ (og'zini yopmoq). Quyida struktural frazeologik sinonimlarda tarkibiy qism almashtirilishi ifodaviy kuchaytiruvchi va shu bilan birga ma'no jihatdan farqlovchi funksiyani bajaradi: Masalan: *jmdm. fällt ein Stein vom Herzen, jmdm. fällt ein Steinbruch vom Herzen* - „jmd. ist sehr erleichtert über etwas“ (yelkasidan tog' ag'darilmoq – biror bir ishning yengillashishi).

Oxir-oqibatda frazeologizm tarkibiy qismlarning o'zgarishi hududlarga qarab o'zgarishi ham mumkin: Masalan: *Nur die allerdümmsten Kälber wählen sich den Schlächter selber* (Sprichw., Gemeinpr.) (adabiy tilda). *Nur die allerdümmsten Kälber wählen sich den Metzger selber* (schwäb., bair.) (Shvabiya va Bavariya dialektida) - qo'chqor tayoq yegisi kelsa, choponning tayog'iga suyanadi.

Keltirilgan misollardan shu ayon bo'ladiki, o'zgaruvchan tarkibiy qismlar frazeologizmlarning ichki tuzilmasini shakllantiruvchi markaziy elementalr jumlasiga kiradi. Aynan shu omil farqlovchi kuch hosil qiladi va shunday frazeologizmlarni hosil qiladiki, ular

tilga olingan jihatlari bo'yicha bir-biridan farq qiladi hamda shu mezonlar orqali sinonimlarga qo'yilgan mezonlarga javob beradi.

Agar tarkibiy qismlarning o'zgarishi frazeologizmlarning ichki tuzilmasini o'zgartirmasa, ya'ni iboraning tasviri mohiyatan saqlanib qolsa, u holda ushbu holatga struktural sinonimlar deb emas, balki struktural variantlar deb qaraladi. Bularga o'tli tarkibiy qismlarning son kategoriyasidagi o'zgarish, predloglarning (ko'makchilarning) o'zgarishi, ayrim frazeologik birikmalarda (juft so'zlarda) tarkibiy qismlarning o'rin almashishi va boshqalar kiradi. Masalan: *ein Haar - Haare in der Suppe finden* – tirnoq ostidan kir qidirmoq; *die Hand - die Hände bei etw. im Spiel(e) haben* – biror bir ishda qo'li bor bo'lmoq; *etw. brennt jmdm. auf den Nägeln - etw. brennt jmdm. unter den Nägeln* - ma'nosi: juda zarur bo'lgan, muhim va shoshilinch masala; *nichts auf den Rippen haben - nichts zwischen den Rippen haben*- ma'nosi: juda ozg'in bo'lish; *groß und klein - klein und groß* - katta va kichik; kichik va katta; *auf Leben und Tod- auf Tod und Leben* (ma'nosi: nihoyatda jiddiy, hal qiluvchi).

Frazeologik struktur sinonimlar va variantlarning bu kabi tahlili til bilan birgalikda uyg'unlashadi, chunki frazeologiyada ma'nodosh sinonimlarning nafaqat miqdori ko'p, balki bu yo'l bilan ular doimiy ravishda kengayib boradi. Go'yoki bir-biriga ziddek tuyulgan ushbu hodisaning sababi shundaki, ma'nodosh sinonimlar semantik uslubiy xususiyat nuqtai nazaridan bir-birini o'rnini bosa olsa ham, baribir ular bir xil emas. Ushbu sinonim so'zlari ma'nolarining qanday sabab bilan paydo bo'lganligi yoki shakli har doim bir biridan farq qiladi. Masalan: *alles über einen Leisten schlagen, alles über einen Kamm scheren, alles in einen Topf werfen* - "alles gleich behandeln und dabei wichtige Unterschiede nicht beachten" - barchaga bir xil munosabatda bo'lish. Yoki masalan: *mit jmdm. ein Hühnchen zu rupfen haben, mit jmdm. eine Rübe zu schaben haben, mit jmdm. ein Nüsschen zu knacken haben* - „jmdn. wegen etw. zur Rechenschaft ziehen müssen“ - kim bilandir hisob-kitob qilib olish. Shunday qilib, ma'nodosh frazeologik sinonimlar frazeologizmlarning metaforik asosga ega bo'lishi jihatidan farqlanadi va aynan shu farqlik paradigmatic xususiyatning saqlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari, yuqorida keltilgan sinonimik qatorlar frazeologik sinonimiya yana bir o'ziga xos jihatini – yani semantik dominant yoki asosiy sinonimning tushib qolganligini ham ko'rsatadi. Ma'lumki, leksik sinonimlar qatorining asosiy sinonimi ushbu qatorning markaziy bo'g'inini tashkil etadi, qolgan sinonimlar esa undan ikkilamchi belgilari orqali farq qiladi. Ko'pincha bosh sinonim uslubiy jihatdan belgisiz bo'ladi va uning markaziy xususiyati aynan undan – ya'ni asosiy sinonimdan – yangi va qo'shma so'zlarning yasalishi orqali yanada aniqroq namoyon bo'ladi. Guvohi bo'lganimizdek, frazeologiyadagi bunday sinonimik qator tuzilmasini yaratishning imkoni yo'q, chunki barcha frazeologik sinonimlar o'z semantikasi tufaydi uslubiy jihatdan belgilagan bo'ladi va bunday qatordan birliklarning o'zgarmas (invariant) bosh ma'nosi faqat bitta leksik birlik (leksema) asosida aniqlanishi mumkin, bu yondashuvni birinchi marta tilshunos olim Sh. Balli ilgari surgan.

Shunday qilib frazeologik sinonimlar nemis tilida tildagi so'z boyligini orttirishdan tashqari nutqni jozibali, emotsional va tushunarli hamda fikrni to'liq bayon qilishda qo'l keladi.

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СЕМАНТИКА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ (ФЕ) РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА С КОМПОНЕНТАМИ ЦИФРЫ

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена семантике фразеологических единиц (ФЕ) русского языка с компонентами цифры. При анализе семантики ФЕ русского языка с числовым компонентом основной упор делался на материале русских фразеологических словарей и некоторых известных работ великих учёных.

Ключевые слова: семантика, фразеологические единицы, число, лингвистика, область, устойчивость фразеологических единиц, структура фразеологизмов.

Annotation: The article is devoted to the semantics of phraseological units (PU) of the Russian language with numeral components. When analyzing the semantics of phraseological units of the Russian language with a numerical component, the main emphasis was placed on the material of Russian phraseological dictionaries and some well-known works of great scientists.

Key words: semantics, phraseological units, number, linguistics, area, stability of phraseological units, structure of phraseological units.

Фразеология – такая область языкознания, которая в наименьшей степени используется при изучении как родного, так и иностранных языков. Но именно этот пласт лексики дает наиболее точное представление об этнокультурном и языковом характере того или иного народа-носителя языка. Следовательно, можно полагать, что тема настоящего анализа актуальна в рамках развития теории и практики культурной коммуникации.

Очевидно, что изучение фразеологического богатства языка способствует более полному постижению сути языка, менталитета народа, говорящего на этом языке.

Цель данной статьи - разносторонний анализ ФЕ русского языка с компонентом-числительным и выявление влияния семантики чисел на значение ФЕ.

С самого начала надлежит отметить, что число не есть счет, но число есть результат счета, при конструктивном понимании числа, и счет есть путь к концепту «Число», при платоническом понимании числа, как объективно существующей сущности, – это концепт «число», который, естественно, связывается с понятием натурального ряда чисел.

В своём философском словаре Лаланд А. отмечает, что последовательность чисел, натуральный ряд чисел, часто смешивается с самим понятием числа, чего не следует делать, и дает важное примечание: «Идея числа предполагает трансформацию последовательности (время) в сумму (пространство). Это последнее условие, по-видимому, самое важное, так как если мы ограничиваемся последовательностью, то имеем дело лишь с рядом или множеством, но ещё не с числом. Этим опровергается различие, которое Кант пытался установить между геометрией, наукой о пространстве,

и арифметикой, наукой о времени, поскольку образование идеи числа требует, в качестве своего условия, формы сосуществования и одновременности» [4, с. 208].

Имеется множество фразеологизмов в русском языке, где одним из компонентов образного выражения является числительное. Причем, как это часто и бывает с фразеологизмами, этот самый компонент утрачивает свое прямое, в данном случае числовое, значение и приобретает смысл неопределенного количества. Иногда неопределенно малого, иногда неопределенно большого и значительного. А чаще всего количественное значение вообще отсутствует или переосмыслено. Например: используя фразеологизм «опять двадцать пять», мы выражаем недовольство по поводу чего-либо много раз повторяющегося и надоевшего, а вовсе не пытаемся утверждать, что этих повторений было именно 25.

Попытаюсь привести ряд фразеологизмов в порядке возрастания числового значения (от нуля – «ничтожества» и единицы – «очень малого и незначительного» к мифической тройке и семерке, выражающей неисчислимо большое множество, и так далее... до ста).

Причем, когда мы говорим о понятии, которое могут передавать те или иные числительные, помните, что исключения бывают очень часто, и закономерности, приводимые здесь, весьма общие и приблизительные [1, с. 128].

Итак: 0 – передает понятие ничтожества (и действительно, в математике это число, от прибавления которого никакое число не меняется).

Абсолютный ноль - человек ничтожный, совершенно бесполезный в каком-либо деле. Круглый ноль (нуль). Прост. Экспрес. Ничего не значащий, не стоящий человек. -Муж твой для тебя -круглый ноль, ты сама это знаешь. К чему тогда все эти слёзы и упрёки? (Чехов. Выгодная сделка). И хотя глядел он умно и строго, ходил с достоинством, а говорил, растягивая слова, Фомич понял, что мужичонко этот -круглый ноль (Б. Можаяев. Живой!) [2, с. 108].

Числительное один означает 1.ничтожно малое количество; 2.одинокость, незначительность, беспомощность; 3.одинаковость, похожесть; 4. единство. Один как перст-одинокий. Один-одиношечек-одинокий; Одним миром мазаны-с одинаковыми недостатками; Одного поля ягода – совершенно похожи по духу, по своему поведению или положению;

На один покрой - одинаковый, подобный; на одну колодку - одинаковый, подобный; На одно лицо - очень похожи друг на друга, лишены индивидуальных, существенных отличий; о ком-либо или о чем-либо; Одним махом-сразу, за один прием. Одной веревочкой связан(ы)-объединен чем-то общим, неразрывным. Одним словом-заклучая что-либо сказанное, «короче говоря»; В один голос:1. все вместе, одновременно (отвечать, спрашивать и т.п.); 2.единодушно, единогласно (утверждать, повторять и т.п.); Мерить на один аршин - подходить к оценке различных людей, явлений, обстоятельств и т.п. одинаково, без учета индивидуальных особенностей; На один зуб-об очень малом количестве еды; Один черт-(груб.)одно и то же, все равно; Один к одному-один лучше другого; Один конец-выражение отчаянной решимости: выбора нет, ждет печальный исход; Один на один-без посторонних; Один шаг до...-совсем близко; Под одну гребенку (стричь всех)-уравнивать всех в каком-либо отношении; Как одна минута-очень быстро; Одна нога здесь, другая там-очень близко; Жить одним домом - вместе, сообща вести хозяйство; Хоть одним глазком - мельком (посмотреть, взглянуть и т.п. на кого-либо или на что-либо); Одним махом/одним духом - разом, быстро выпить или что-либо сделать; Одним росчерком пера - простой подписью под приказом, распоряжением и т.п., обычно не вникая в суть дела,

мгновенно, быстро (делать что-либо); Все до одного - (все) без исключения, полностью; Одной ногой в могиле - близок к смерти; Первая ласточка – самый первый среди подобных или самые ранние признаки появления чего-либо; Первый встречный-случайный человек; 1. мгновенность, быстрота, близость в расстоянии. Фразеологизм одним глазом. Разг. Делая что-либо, присматривать, смотреть за кем-либо, чем-либо. [Официант] оставил поднос, вскарабкался на эстраду. Он поёт о своих любовных неудачах... и одним глазом всё же присматривает, чтобы не ушёл кто, не заплатив за стаканчик (И. Эренбург. Испания) [2, с. 251].

Числительное два означает 1. малое количество; 2. разделение (например: На два фронта); Раз-два да и готово-о чем-то, что можно быстро сделать, приготовить и т.п.; Раз-два да и обчелся-так мало, что можно посчитать (или считать не нужно); В два счета-очень быстро, моментально; без промедления; В двух шагах от...-очень близко; Два сапога – пара-один другого не лучше: Убить двух зайцев-сразу выполнить два нужных, важных дела; добиться осуществления двух целей; Похожи как две капли воды-очень сильно похож; На два слова – (вызвать) коротко оговорить о чем-либо; Черта с два – вовсе нет, этому не бывать; От горшка два вершка-мал ростом или мал по возрасту, неопытен; Из вторых рук - через посредников (узнать, получить и т.п.) (= из третьих рук); Есть в два горла – очень много есть; На два фронта – действовать в двух разных направлениях; Между двух огней – быть в трудном, опасном положении, когда неприятности грозят с двух сторон; Сидеть между двух стульев – находиться в неопределенном положении; Ни два ни полтора – нечто неопределенное; Палка о двух концах - о том, что может кончиться хорошо или плохо; Ясно, как дважды два (четыре). В оба (два, три) глаза смотреть. Разг. Экспрес. С напряжением, вниманием (смотреть). [Рославлев:] От верной-то твоей. Показывал письмо мне Блестов, -в оба глаза смотрел я и читал, и перечёл два раза (Грибоедов. Притворная неверность). -Убит? Веснин?.. - Разве ты не знал, что он непременно в каждое пекло лезет?.. – Не знал? Сдерживать его надо было, смотреть в оба глаза! Какого золотого человека потеряли, а? (Ю. Бондарев. Горячий снег). -Не померещилось тебе там? Бомба ?.. В три глаза смотри! -наставлял мичман. -Не задень! Ну, давай! Ни пуха тебе... (А. Соболев. Фронтное крещение) [2, с. 308].

Числительное четыре используется в фразеологизме в четырех стенах – жить, не выходя из дому. Разг. Экспрес. 1. Ни с кем не общаясь, в полном одиночестве. [Чехов] всегда говорил, что писателю нельзя сидеть в четырёх стенах и вытягивать из себя свои произведения (Телешов. Записки писателя). 2. Не выходя из помещения. [Митя:]Эка тоска. Господи!.. На улице праздник, у всякого в доме праздник, а ты сиди в четырёх стенах! (А. Островский. Бедность не порок[2, с. 308].

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СИМВОЛИКА ЖИВОТНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКИХ СКАЗКАХ И ЕЕ ПЕРЕДАЧА В РУССКОМ ПЕРЕВОДЕ

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Аннотация: В данной работе рассматриваются особенности передачи зоонимов при переводе английских литературных сказок на русский язык. Проанализированы примеры употребления названий животных в оригинальных текстах и их переводах, выявлены случаи буквального и переносного использования зоонимов. Особое внимание уделено сохранению национально-культурной специфики и эмоционально-оценочной окраски при переводе. Результаты исследования показывают, что адекватный перевод зоонимов требует не только лингвистической точности, но и учета культурного контекста, символики и авторского замысла.

Ключевые слова: зооним, перевод, английские литературные сказки, культурный контекст, символика, метафора, эквивалентность, лингвистический анализ.

Abstract: This paper examines the peculiarities of translating zoonyms in English literary fairy tales into Russian. Examples of animal names used in original texts and their translations are analyzed, highlighting both literal and figurative uses. Special attention is given to preserving national and cultural specificity as well as the emotional and evaluative tone. The results show that an adequate translation of zoonyms requires not only linguistic accuracy but also consideration of cultural context, symbolism, and the author's intent.

Key words: zoonym, translation, English literary fairy tales, cultural context, symbolism, metaphor, equivalence, linguistic analysis.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda ingliz adabiy ertaklaridagi zoonimlarning rus tiliga tarjima qilinish xususiyatlari o'rganiladi. Asliy matnlarda va ularning tarjimalarida hayvon nomlarining qo'llanishi tahlil qilinib, ularning so'zma-so'z va ko'chma ma'noda ishlatilish holatlari aniqlangan. Tadqiqotda milliy-madaniy xususiyatlar hamda emotsional-baholovchi ohangni saqlab qolish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, zoonimlarni adekvat tarjima qilish nafaqat lingvistik aniqlikni, balki madaniy kontekst, ramziylik va muallif maqsadini hisobga olishni ham talab etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: zoonim, tarjima, ingliz adabiy ertaklari, madaniy kontekst, ramziylik, metafora, ekvivalentlik, lingvistik tahlil.

Животные сопровождают человека всю его жизнь, занимают важное место в языковой картине мира и нашли широкое отражение в устном народном творчестве, в частности в сказках. Сказки знакомы всем, их интересные и занимательные сюжеты увлекают и очаровывают не только детей, но и взрослых. Э.В. Померанцева в Большой Советской Энциклопедии даёт следующее определение сказки: «Сказка один из основных жанров устного народнопоэтического творчества, эпическое, преимущественно прозаическое художественное произведение волшебного,

авантюрного или бытового характера с установкой на вымысел. Сказкой называют различные виды устной прозы, отсюда разноречивость в определении её жанровых особенностей. От других видов художественной эпики сказка отличается тем, что сказочник подаёт её, а слушатели воспринимают прежде всего, как поэтический вымысел, игру фантазии. Это, однако, не лишает сказку связи с действительностью, определяющей идейное содержание, язык, характер сюжетов, мотивов, образов. Во многих сказках нашли отражение первобытные общественные отношения и представления, тотемизм, анимизм и др.... сказки обладают национальными особенностями, отражают уклад жизни того или иного народа, его труд и быт, природные условия» [7, 1453].

Литературная сказка является наследницей народной. Жанр литературной сказки возник в последней трети XVIII века в эпоху романтизма, когда появился пристальный интерес ко всему народному, национальному. Романтики черпали свои сюжеты из сказок, записанных фольклористами, видели в литературных произведениях народного творчества образцы для подражания. Поэтому она сочетает в себе как черты народного фольклора, так и элементы литературных жанров.

Существует несколько научных определений литературной или авторской сказки, отражающих её идейно-художественное своеобразие. Так, Л.Ю.Брауде видит в литературной сказке «авторское художественное прозаическое или поэтическое произведение, основанное либо на фольклорных источниках, либо придуманное самим писателем, но в любом случае подчиненное его воле; произведение, преимущественно фантастическое, рисующее приключения вымышленных или традиционных сказочных героев и в некоторых случаях ориентированное на детей»; произведение, в котором «волшебство, чудо играет роль сюжетобразующего фактора, помогает охарактеризовать персонажей», подчеркивая при этом, что литературная сказка принадлежит своему времени, и не может иметь универсального определения т.к. содержание и направление такой сказки постоянно изменяются даже в рамках творчества одного и того же писателя. Каждая историческая эпоха или литературное направление рождает новую художественную форму [2,7].

А.Б.Бритаева обобщила опыт предыдущих лингвистов, и ее определение «литературная сказка – это многовариантный жанр художественного словотворчества, произведение с фантастическим сюжетом, оригинальной авторской концепцией, основанное на синтезе фольклорных и литературных традиций и преследующее эстетические цели» [3] мы считаем наиболее полным. В следствие того, что литературная сказка возникла на основе народной, она сохраняет ряд фольклорных традиций, в частности систему образов, и мы нередко можем встретить животных в качестве действующих героев, родовая характеристика которых является предметом нашего исследования.

Что такое зооним - Слова, обозначающие разных представителей животного мира, весьма многообразны и принадлежат к одному из наиболее интересных пластов лексики современного английского языка. Они издавна привлекали внимание исследователей. В лингвистической литературе подобные слова известны как анимализмы или зоонимы. Мы в своей работе будем использовать термин зооним.

Лингвисты дают различные определения зоонимов. Т.В. Хахалкина под зоонимами понимает «...собственно названия животных в прямом номинативном значении» [9]. Н. В. Располюхина придерживается того же мнения [9]. Е.В. Метельская отмечает, что термин «зооним» имеет популярность в современной лингвистике и «... является общим наименованием представителей фауны – птиц, млекопитающих,

насекомых и рептилий» [13]. Итак, под термином «зооним» нами понимается «Наименование представителя животного мира» [8].

Категория рода зоонимов в английском языке. Зоонимы в английском языке, как и в других индоевропейских языках относятся к существительным, которые обладают категорией рода. Грамматический род слова обычно связывают с полом обозначаемого им существа. Советский Энциклопедический Словарь определяет грамматический род как традиционное название одной из групп, на которые делятся существительные в зависимости от способа согласования с ними прилагательных, глаголов и др. (муж. жен. и ср. род, в некоторых языках – муж. и жен. род, возможен также общий род). Категория рода развилась на базе первоначальной семантической классификации по признакам «живое – неживое» и (или) «мужской – женский пол». При этом отмечается, что в некоторых языках категория рода отсутствует. [13, 1142].

В древнеанглийском языке род существительных выражался морфологически и отражал синтаксические связи между словами посредством их согласования в роде. Но уже к концу среднеанглийского периода (середина XII – конец XIV веков) морфологические показатели категории рода, в основном, были утрачены. Многие исследователи считают, что в современном английском языке категории рода не существует. Например, Б.А.Ильиш отрицает наличие данной категории на основании того факта, что ни одно существительное в современном английском языке не проявляет никаких морфологических особенностей в своей принадлежности к мужскому или женскому роду [6, с.36]

Гуревич В.В. считает, что, если у существительных нет соответствующих грамматических показателей (окончаний), то соответственно нет и грамматической категории рода. В тех же случаях, где род существительного различается - это категория семантическая, а не грамматическая, поскольку ни у самого существительного, ни у определения к нему формальных показателей рода нет. Род определяется лишь по соотношению с личным местоимением 3 л. ед. ч. (he, she, it) [5, с.138].

Однако, некоторые современные лингвисты предпочитают рассматривать род существительных как отдельную категорию. Так, Гордон Е.М. и Крылова И.П. выделяют три рода: мужской (masculine), женский (feminine) и средний (или нейтральный) (neuter).

К мужскому роду относятся существительные, обозначающие представителей мужского пола (a man – мужчина, a boy – мальчик), которые могут заменяться местоимением he (он).

К женскому роду относятся существительные, обозначающие представителей женского пола (a woman – женщина, a girl – девочка), заменяемые местоимением she (она).

Все остальные существительные и представители фауны в том числе относятся к среднему роду, и могут заменяться личным местоимением 'it' (оно) [4, с.205]. Однако, если хотят указать пол животного или речь идет о домашнем питомце, то употребляется местоимение 'she' или 'he'. При этом Борсов М.Ю. отмечает, что для родовой категоризации зоонимов в английском языке очень важную роль играют стереотипы, поскольку соотношение какого-либо слова с социальным родом происходит на основе стереотипной классификации. Все активное и сильное является признаком мужского начала, а все слабое и пассивное является характеристикой для всего женского [1].

Итак, мы можем сделать вывод, что в английском языке родовую категоризацию зоонимов следует признать произвольной, поскольку формальных характеристик принадлежности тех или иных зоонимов к какому-либо роду не существует, при этом

одно и то же животное может соотноситься как с местоимением женского рода, так и с местоимением мужского рода, причем этот выбор зависит либо от намерений автора, либо диктуется нормами и традициями сказочных произведений.

Переводческие трансформации при переводе зоонимов, род которых не совпадает с их эквивалентами в русском языке

Используя метод сплошной выборки, в выше названных литературных сказках мы выделили более 30 зоонимов, чей род не совпадает с их эквивалентами в русском языке.

По традиции местоимение 'it', относящееся к среднему роду, довольно часто используется авторами для родовой категоризации своих персонажей. В данном случае автор не воспринимает их как персонажей, имеющих особенные характеристики лиц мужского или женского пола, и переводчики используют местоимение того рода, которое соответствует роду этого слова в русском языке. Например, в «Алисе в стране чудес» Л. Кэрролла зоониму 'mouse' в переводе соответствует 'мышь', относящееся по нормам русского языка к женскому роду:

The Mouse looked at her rather inquisitively, and seemed to her to wink with one of its little eyes, but it said nothing [14]. – Мышь взглянула на нее с недоумением и легонько ей подмигнула (так, во всяком случае, показалось Алисе), но не сказала в ответ ни слова [13].

Рассмотрим следующий пример:

The Cat only grinned when it saw Alice [14].

На первый взгляд кажется, что употребленное автором местоимения 'it' с зоонимом 'Cheshire cat' дает переводчику свободу для выбора рода этого существа, но переводчики переводят данный зооним мужским родом: «Завидев Алису, Кот только улыбнулся» [13], т.к. в английской языковой культуре зооним 'cat' преимущественно осмысливается в мужском роде.

Однако иногда русский эквивалент английского зоонима, принадлежащего к среднему роду, может вступать в противоречие с его контекстуальной родовой характеристикой:

«...at last the Caterpillar took the hookah out of its mouth, and addressed her in a languid, sleepy voice. 'Who are YOU?' said the Caterpillar» [14].

Притяжательное местоимение "its" указывает на средний род зоонима 'caterpillar'. В русском языке ему соответствует слово 'гусеница', принадлежащее к женскому роду. Но в разговоре Алиса обращается к ней 'сэр': «I- I hardly know, sir...» [14], поэтому мы можем сказать, что по контексту данный зооним относится к мужскому роду.

Б. Заходер стремится сохранить в своем переводе род зоонима и заменяет эквивалент 'гусеница' на 'червяк':

... наконец Червяк вынул изо рта чубук и сонно, медленно произнес:

– Кто – ты – такая?

– Видите ли... видите ли, сэр, я... просто не знаю ...[12].

Н. Демурова же следует нормам русского языка и переводит зооним, заменяя мужской род на женский и обращение 'сэр' на 'сударыня':

Гусеница вынула кальян изо рта и медленно, словно в полусне, заговорила:

– Ты ... кто... такая? – спросила Синяя Гусеница.

Начало не очень-то располагало к беседе.

– Сейчас, право, не знаю, сударыня, – отвечала Алиса [13].

Подобную трансформацию мы можем увидеть, анализируя контекст сказки О. Уайльда «Счастливый принц». ‘Swallow’ (ласточка) относится автором к мужскому роду, т.к. замещается в тексте личным местоимением мужского рода ‘he’ и соответствующим ему притяжательным ‘him’:

Итак, анализ перевода зоонимов, род которых не совпадает в английском и русском языках, выявил следующие переводческие трансформации:

1. зоонимы, замещаемые местоимением среднего рода ‘it’, переводятся мужским или женским родом, следуя нормам русского языка, но с учетом культурных традиций английского;
2. замена английского зоонима на подходящий аналог;
3. замещение женского рода мужским и наоборот;
4. нулевой перевод;
5. добавления.

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СТРУКТУРА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ(ФЕ) С СОМАТИЧЕСКИМ КОМПОНЕНТОМ «ДАЪОН-РОТ»

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Аннотация. Данной статье анализируются структура фразеологических единиц(ФЕ) с соматическим компонентом «даъон-рот». Даъон-рот – основной части тело человека, а именно часть лица. Для описания или характеристики этой часть органа употребляется такие ФЕ таджикского языка как: **даъон яла кардан** (букв. открыть рот) в знач. прозевать и др.

Ключевые слова: структура, характеристика, часть лица, компонент, фразеологическая единица, таджикский язык.

Abstract. This article analyzes the structure of phraseological units (PUs) with the somatic component “*даъон-рот*” (*mouth*). The mouth is one of the main parts of the human body, specifically a part of the face. To describe or characterize this organ, Tajik language uses phraseological units such as *даъон яла кардан* (literally “to open one’s mouth”) meaning *to yawn*, and others.

Keywords: structure, characteristic, part of the face, component, phraseological unit, Tajik language.

Фразеологизм является одним из самых актуальных и частотных объектов современных лингвоантропологических исследований. Это обусловлено тем, что в нем наиболее ярким образом проявляется субъективный человеческий фактор, отражающий лингвокреативный потенциал человеческого мышления. При изучении фразеологизма в диаде «фразеологический знак - человек» точкой отсчёта в лингвистическом анализе становится человек, определяющий и перспективу, и конечные цели этого анализа.

Во фразеобразовании огромную роль играет человеческий фактор, так как подавляющее большинство фразеологизмов связано с человеком, с разнообразными сферами его деятельности. Фактор адресата является важнейшим элементом коммуникации. Кроме того, человек стремится наделить человеческими чертами объекты внешнего мира, в том числе и неодушевлённые. Ещё Ш. Балли утверждал: "Извечное несовершенство человеческого разума проявляется также и в том, что человек всегда стремится одухотворить то, что его окружает. Он не может представить себе, что природа мертва и бездушна; его воображение постоянно наделяет жизнью неодушевлённые предметы, но это ещё не всё: человек постоянно приписывает всем предметам внешнего мира черты и стремления, свойственные его личности" [1, с.26].

Особую роль в этих коммуникационных процессах играют соматические фразеологические единицы. Соматическую фразеологию образуют фразеологические единицы, один из компонентов которых - название части тела человека или животного.

Характерной чертой соматической фразеологии является наличие в языке многочисленных аналогов, очень близких по образной направленности словосочетаний. Эта особенность резко отличает соматические фразеологизмы от других тематических групп фразеологических единиц. Совпадение образности соматических фразеологизмов, наличие в языке многочисленных аналогов, очень близких по образной направленности словосочетаний приводят к возникновению близких фразеологических единиц, демонстрирующих универсальный характер переноса соматических лексем, их функционально-семантическую динамику в составе фразеологических единиц таджикского языка.

В таджикском языке для обозначения части тела имеются следующие лексемы: сар-голова, даст-рука, руй-лицо, гўш-ухо, дахон-рот, бинй-рот, гардан-шея, чигар-печень, дил-сердце, пой-нога, бадан-тело, гулў-горло, забон-язык и т.д. В данной статье нами анализируются фразеологических единиц таджикского языка с компонентом «дањон-рот»

Дањон-рот – основной части тело человека, а именно часть лица. Для описания или характеристики этого часть органа употребляется такие ФЕ таджикского языка как: **дањон яла кардан** (букв. открыть рот) в знач. прозевать; **дањону бинй дар льяш** (букв. рот и нос на месте) в знач. всё на месте; **дањон монанди писта** (букв. рот как фисташка) в знач. красивый ротик и т.п.

Дањон-рот – основной части тело человека выполняет функции говорение и употребление пищи. Следовательно, основная семантика ФЕ с компонентом дањон выражает действия этого органа. Употребление термина в составе ФЕ со значение «пытаться выведать» основано на метонимическом переносе, в результате которого рот ассоциируется с речью: дањони касеро поидан (букв. ждать чьё-л рот) в знач. в ожидании слов; дањони касе тасфидан (букв. чей-то язык накаляться) в знач. заговориться

В данной лексико-семантической группе выделяются блок ФЕ с компонентом рот со значением «болтливость» оцениваемая как положительно, так и отрицательно: даъони касе шалақ будан в знач. болтливый: аз даъонатон асал / (букв. из вашего рта мёд) в знач. красноречив. В ФЕ со значением «сквернословие» рот осмысляется как испорченный, со сломанным механизмом, черный или плохо пахнущий: даъон олонидан (букв. пачкать рот) в знач. ругаться.

В составе ФЕ в значения «молчаливость» компонент даъон-рот выступает как метафорическая замена процесса говорения: даъон пӯшидан (букв. закрыть рот) в знач. молчать; ба даъон об гирифта (букв. в рот взять воду) в знач. молчать. Здесь наблюдается метафорическое переосмысление путём ассоциирования процесса говорения со ртом; реализуется значение слова даъон, связанное с её непосредственным участием в осуществлении вербальной коммуникации: даъонро маҳкам пӯштан (букв. закрыть рот) в знач. молчать.

Лексема даъон-рот в составе ФЕ со значением «быть широко известным» также выступает как метафорическая замена процесса говорения. ФЕ с данным значением несут отрицательную оценку: даъон хоидан (букв. жевать рот) в знач. невнятно, уклончиво. Как указано выше, другой функцией рта является употребление пищи. Употребление лексемы даъон-рот в значении даъон-рот как орган приема пищи основано на этой функции рта. Лексико-фразеологический уровень языка располагает огромными возможностями для передачи информации в ее тончайших смысловых и стилистических оттенках [2, с. 6].

Семантика слова даъон-рот как «врата тело» образовано путем метафорического переноса – рот осмыляется как ворота, через которые душа, сердце и печень, проявляя на эмоциональные переживания, могут информироваться с внешним миром: рӯдаш / льигараш ба даъон омад (букв. кишка/печень пришла в рот) в знач. переживание. Данный вид переноса основан на сходстве « по форме: рот как отверстие, являющееся проходом в замкнутый объем» каковым мыслится человек» лексема даъон –рот может осмыляться также как посредник между сердцем, умом:

В данной ФЕ осложнен коннотативный аспект всего фразового единства, связанного с высказыванием наболевшего, лишённого прикрас содержания душевной жизни человека.

Путем сопоставления **даъон-рот** с забон-язык осуществляется характеристика личностных свойств человека: дар даъонаш забон надорад (букв. во рту не имеет языка) в знач. молчаливый.

Описание симптоматики эмоций также происходит при участии **даъон-рот** в ФЕ:

даъон то гӯша (букв. рот до ушей) счастливый и т.д.

Узко-частный фразеологический факт соединения с существительным даъон выполняющим функцию стержневого компонента:

даъон кушодан. в знач. заговорить;

даъонкалонӣ кардан в знач. кичиться;

даъони худро гундоштан в знач. молчать.

Количество подобных ФЕ со стержневым компонентом даъон-рот более 60. Следует отметить, что лексика, обозначающая частей тела человека – соматизмы, именно даъон-рот как стержневой компонент активно участвует в образовании ФЕ таджикского языка, этим и обогащает словарный фонд таджикского языка.

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ТРАКТОВКИ ТЕРМИНА «МАЪНАВИЯТ» В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация. В этой статье анализируются глубокие реформы, появившиеся по вопросам терминов после обретения Независимости, когда узбекскому языку был присвоен статус государственного языка. Термины подверглись изменениям с точки зрения качества, сущности, значения.

Ключевые слова: термины, форма и содержание, процесс использования, эквивалент, типичный, литературный словарь.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада Мустақиллик даврига келиб, хусусан, ўзбек тилига давлат тили мақоми берилгандан сўнг атамалар масаласида туб ислохот юзага келди. Атамалар сифат, яъни мазмун-моҳиятига кўра ўзгаришларга учрагани ҳақидаги долзарб масалага бағишланган.

Калит сўзлар: атамалар, шакл ва мазмун, қўллаш жараёни, эквивалент, типик, адабиётшунослик луғат.

Annotation. This article has undergone fundamental reform in terms of terms since independence and in particular when the Uzbek language was given the status of a state language. Terms deal with the urgent issue of quality, that is, changes in meaning.

Keywords: terms, form and content, use process, equivalent, typical, literary dictionary.

Во всех науках терминология является базовым словом и ключом, обозначающим сущность, законы и категории одной и той же науки. В этом смысле нет такой области науки, чтобы ее термины не были разработаны и опубликованы в виде отдельной книги. К моменту обретения независимости, особенно после того, как узбекский язык получил статус государственного, произошла радикальная реформа в вопросе терминов, что было вполне естественно.

Термины изменились не только с точки зрения количества, но и с точки зрения качества, то есть содержания. Уже доказано наукой, что изменение лексики и терминологии происходит быстро. Поэтому мы считаем, что научное исследование изменений формы и содержания пришло к абстрактному выводу.

В результате изменений, произошедших в узбекском языкознании в конце XX и начале XXI веков, были созданы широкие возможности для выполнения задач, поставленных перед национальным языком, особое внимание уделяется разработке лингвистических принципов адекватных межъязыковых сравнений, выражающих единицы различных концептов в лингвистике. В настоящее время с целью обеспечения полного внедрения государственного языка в нашей стране «...введение в оборот научно-обоснованных новых слов и терминов, создание узбекских альтернатив современных терминов и обеспечения их широкого применения, поддержка научно-исследовательских работ по развитию государственного языка, осуществление международного сотрудничества в данной сфере » [1.].

Слова с духовно-нравственным содержанием являются частью высокой лексики русского языка, недаром М.В. Ломоносов включил их в «высокий штиль» и

в дальнейшем изучалась и отражалась в Российской русистике

(С.И. Ожегов, В.В.Виноградов, О.С Ахманова, , НМ Шанский, НМ. Шведова и др). Традиционные духовно-нравственные концепты усваиваются сознанием, передаются следующим поколениям, что способствует сохранению отечественной духовной культуры.

В мировой лингвистике проведено множество исследований по изучению сущности понятия «маънавият»(«духовность»), такими учеными как Л.Ньюман, Р.Таньи, Т.Гаак, С.Конновой, К.Колкуновой, Т.Малевича, В.Костомарова. Также существуют другие исследования, посвященные проблеме «духовности» в рамках социально-гуманитарных наук. В узбекском языкознании развитие духовно-просветительской лексики узбекского языка в годы независимости частично изучено Г.Тожиевой, М. Б. Ахмедовой, Ф. Х. Юлдашевым, однако в данном направлении других исследований нет.

С первых лет независимости Узбекистана духовность стала национальным вопросом в качестве главного условия развития общества.

Понятие «духовность» имеет двойкий смысл: религиозное и светское. Поле «духовность» имеет неоднородную структуру: нравственность, патриотизм, благодать, блаженный, вера, дух, душа, истина, крест, любовь, ответственность, совесть, спасение, справедливость, целомудрие, честность.

В узбекском языке отсутствует альтернатива термина «маънавият» и отсутствие его точной альтернативы в русском языке. Выражение «маънавият» переводится на русский язык как духовность. Однако их лексикографическая трактовка, не подходит к выражению слова «маънавият» и, дает значение лексемы «рухият» в узбекском языке.

Причиной разной трактовки термина «маънавият» в узбекском языке является в большей степени реалии явления и отсутствие его точной альтернативы в других языках. Сущность выражения имеет национальную особенность и является реалией. Реалии, по определению С. Влахова и С. Флорина, это "...слова (и словосочетания) народного языка, представляющие собой наименования предметов, понятий, явлений, характерных для географической среды, культуры, материального быта или общественно-исторических особенностей народа, нации, страны, племени и являющиеся, таким образом, носителями национального, местного или исторического колорита"[2.]. Известно, что перевод реалий невозможен. Эта проблема решается путем передачи смысла на основе контекста.

Отсутствие в 2-х томном «Толковом словаре узбекского языка» самого термина «маънавият» является самым точным доказательством того, какое было отношение к данному вопросу до Независимости. Представление в этом словаре слова маънавий (духовный) (1-том, 454-страница) демонстрирует существование данного понятия в социальном сознании лишь в виде признака и не имевшего статуса действительности. Причиной этому может служить отсутствие альтернативы слова «маънавият» в русском и других европейских языках. В советский период в лексическом сознании узбекского народа хоть и существовал концепт «маънавият», но языковой «шаблон» этого концепта, его выражение не было социализировано. Это доказывается изучением материалов толкового и энциклопедического словарей узбекского языка. Даже в «Толковом словаре узбекского языка»³⁰ не было лексемы «маънавият». Однако в словаре лексема «маънавий» была комментирована следующим образом: Маънавий (а) 1. Относительно внутренней духовной жизни человека. Духовные потребности. Моральная помощь. Ёш ўқитувчининг ҳар бир иши

зағчақўз домлага маънавий жихатдан ҳам, моддий жихатдан ҳам зарба эди. П.Турсун, Ўқитувчи. 2. айн.моральное. Моральный облик человека.

Причиной разной трактовки термина «маънавият» в узбекском языке является в большей степени реалии явления и отсутствие его точной альтернативы в других языках. Например, выражение «маънавият» на английский язык переводится как термин “spirituality”, а на русский язык как духовность. Однако их лексикографическая трактовка, по сути, не подходит к выражению слова «маънавият» и, как правило, дают значение лексемы «руҳият» в узбекском языке. Обращаем внимание: «Духовность – и, ж. Свойство души, состоящее в преобладании духовных, нравственных и интеллектуальных интересов над материальными». Но если перевести дословно «духовность» на узбекский язык, то получится не «маънавият», а «руҳият» или «руҳоният» и будет близко к психологии, точнее, к религиозной психологии. Это доказывает, что сущность выражения имеет национально-ментальную особенность и является по большей части убежденной реалией. Известно, что перевод реалий невозможен и задача решается путем передачи смысла на основе примечаний.

В его структуре проявляется изоморфизм семантического и концептуального полей. Концептуальное поле «духовность» представляет собой совокупность духовно-нравственных концептов, при этом концепт «духовность» является именем поля и макроконцептом по отношению к ментальным единицам в его составе. Соотносимое с ним семантическое поле состоит из единиц духовно-нравственной лексики. Компонентный анализ данной лексико-семантической группы показал, что в своем составе они имеют общий интегральный признак «понятие духовности» и различаются по дифференциальным признакам «религиозная сфера», «этическая сфера», «аксиологические категории» и др. Единицы поля «духовность» находятся, кроме прочего, в отношении гипонимии, имя поля *духовность* является гиперонимом. Состав центральной зоны лингвокультурного поля «духовность» в русской языковой картине мира необычайно широк.

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ЛЕКСИЧЕСКАЯ КУЛЬТУРНАЯ ЕДИНИЦА И ЛИНГВОПОЭТИЧЕСКАЯ ОСОБЕННОСТЬ ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНО ЯЗЫКА ДАСТАНА

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Аннотация. В данной статье на примерах, взятых из языка эпоса, анализируются лексические и культурные единицы, характерные для языка эпоса «Холдор-хан», в частности, явление синонимии, специфичное для стиля эпоса, своеобразие стиля бахши, их составная структура.

Ключевые слова: синонимы, одиночный, парный, сложные синонимы, синонимический ряд.

Abstract. In this article, using examples taken from the language of the epic, lexical and cultural units characteristic of the language of the epic “Kholdor Khan” are analyzed, in particular, the phenomenon of synonymy specific to the style of the epic, the originality of the bakhshi style, and their compositional structure.

Keywords: synonyms, singular, double, compound synonyms, synonymous series.

Язык, сформировавшийся в определенном обществе будет продолжать развиваться. Изучение народного эпоса, считающегося нашим духовным достоянием, особенно его красивого, богатого и уникального языка, сравнивая их с нынешним литературным языком сделать определенные выводы может создать возможность выразить некоторые идеи для лингвистики. В настоящее время в связи с присвоением узбекскому языку статуса государственного языка в результате выхода из употребления иноязычных слов [в основном заимствовано из русского языка] вводятся многие лексические единицы национального языка и его диалектов. Известно, что внутренние возможности сыграли важную роль во всестороннем обогащении языка. В связи с этим целесообразно изучить лексику народных эпосов и ввести в литературный язык необходимые, жизнеспособные слова.

По изучению языка народного эпоса проведен ряд научных исследований¹. Но произведения устного народного творчества, особенно, народные эпосы, настолько обширны, что изучение каждой их капли является одной из важных задач на будущее. Раз так, и изучение лексических культурных единиц, характерных для языка народного эпоса может внести вклад развитию нашего языка. Потому что читатель, читая каждое эпическое произведение, не сразу понимает значение различных слов [архаический, исторический, разговорный, диалектный] в нем, с какой целью они употребляются. А между тем, эти слова принадлежат языку наших предков в прошлом, и большинство из них не вошли в лексикон узбекского литературного языка. Но они встречаются в исторических и диалектных словарях узбекского языка. Раз так, целесообразно знать их этимологию и лексическое значение. Принимая во внимание вышеизложенное, мы сочли необходимым сделать некоторые комментарии по поводу лексических культурных единиц, принадлежащих языку эпоса «Холдор-хан» Эргаша Джуманбулбула.

В современном языкознании слова по форме и значению делятся на синонимы, омонимы и антонимы. Эти термины пришли из русского языкознания в начале

¹ Ш.Шоабдурахмонов. “Равшан” достонининг бадий тили хақида, К.Д.Тошкент, 1949; Х.Абдурахмонов. халк оғзаки асарлари тилининг синтактик хусусиятлари. Тошкент, 1978; С.Турсунов “Алпомиш” достонининг лексик хусусиятлари, К.Д. Тошкент, 1990. 2. У.Жуманазарова. Фозил шоир достонлари тилининг лексик-стилистик қатламлари. –Т.2012. Г.Жуманазарова. Фозил Йўлдош ўғли достонлари тилининг лингвопоэтикаси. Т., 2012 ва бошқалар.

прошлого века. Но бахши использовали такие языковые явления тысячи лет назад. Значит, в результате внедрения со стороны бахши в язык эпоса различных слов из народного языка и диалектов по отношению к словам в современном литературном языке возник новый синонимический ряд омонимов и антонимов. Было бы полезно изучить их в сравнении с литературным языком и принять некоторые из них как литературные нормы. Докажем свою точку зрения примерами из эпического языка.

Например, слово *юртбоши* или *шах* образовало в эпическом языке следующую синонимическую линию со своими историческими и поэтическими вариантами: *шоҳ* (*шах*), *сардор* (*предводитель*), *подшой-олам* (*надшах всего мира*), *султони бокарам* (*султан всего мира*), *юртнинг эгаси* (*владыка страны*), *пушти паноҳ* (*покровитель*), *хон* (*хан*), *хақон* (*правитель*) каби. 1. Ўлим ҳақ, буйруғи шоҳу гадога [8-бет]. 2. Эй подшой олам, султони бокарам [6-бет]. 3. Арзима қулоқ сол, Чамбил сардори [136-бет]. 4. Арзима қулоқ сол, юртнинг эгаси [32-бет]. 5. Маккамсан, Мадинам – қиблагоҳимсан, Арзима қулоқ сол Чамбилнинг хони [136-бет]. 6. Бирови ҳақондир, бирови кашвар [152-бет]. 7. У, ёрон энди мен сизларга пушти паноҳ бўлолмайдиган бўлдим [193-бет].

Видно, что все слова или сочетания слов в приведенных примерах в той или иной степени означают правителя страны. Бахши очень умело пользовался ими, что во многом способствовало привлекательности, богатству и богатству языка произведения. Раз так, некоторые формы этого синонимического ряда должны быть включены в лексикон узбекского языка, чтобы мы имели право выбирать их. Самое интересное, что некоторые из них имеют место в сегодняшнем активном лексиконе. Например, во времена бывшего союза использование слова «министр» (*визирь*) было ужасным явлением. А на сегодняшний день это слово стало повседневным словом. Неудивительно, что если такова судьба ряда слов, употребляемых в языке эпосов.

Слова-синонимы, используемые на языке эпоса отличаясь своей простотой, выразительностью, образностью, служат решению определенных стилистических задач. Например: *Ҳаммани олиб жўнаганимизни мабодо ёв эшитса, ҳаммадан ёмон, каттиқ душман баччағар Райҳон у ҳам бир бало* (123-бет). В приведенном выше примере слова *недруг* и *враг* являясь синонимами, если анализировать его с точки зрения эмоционально-выразительного цвета, *враг* нейтрального цвета, а *недруг* имеет эмоциональную окраску. Слова в синонимическом ряду имеют различное отношение к стилю, слово «ёв» (*недруг*) в данном примере характерно как для поэтического, так и для разговорного стиля. Если привести синонимический ряд этих слов: *душман* (*враг*), *ёв* (*недруг*), *ғаним* (*противник*). Слово *враг* (*душман*) в этом синонимическом ряду нейтральное, общеупотребительное слово, остальные имеют какие-то свои признаки-особенности. *Гўрўғлибек бардош бериб, Сабр қилар ҳар кимга* [123-бет]. Слова «выносливость» и «терпение» в этом примере являются синонимами, имеют разные формы, но имеют одно и то же объединяющее значение. Например: слова *выносливость*, *терпение*, *выдержка*, *воздержанность*, *стойкость* составляют синонимический ряд этих слов. В общем положении, они означают «терпение, выносливость». Но когда они используются отдельно, они выражают уникальное значение. Терпение здесь является доминирующим словом.

Если сосредоточиться на примерах, взятых из эпического языка:

1. *Жуда ботир халқ боради, Урушда бил мард туради.*[126]. 2. *Мирза аскар полвон эди, Бир юракли арслон эди.*(169) *Ғазо деб бари йўл тортиб, Кўринг ботирлар жўнади.*[136] 3. *Қўлида қиличи ботир-баҳодир, Икки ёқни сирпай борур қон сочиб.*[136]

Как видно из приведенных выше примеров, слова «силач» и «богатырь» употребляются в эпосе в значении «смелый» и «храбрый» мастерски использованы бахши во многих местах эпоса. В некоторых местах слово арслон (*отважный*) употребляется также как синоним слов храбрый, смелый, сильный, богатырь.

Синонимы, используемые в эпическом языке, имеют свою структуру. По структуре их можно разделить на простые и сложные синонимы. Простые синонимы являются синонимами, выраженными с помощью отдельных слов. Например, такие слова, как жасур (*смелый*), ботир (*храбрый*), полвон (*сильный*), арслон (*отважный*), мард (*мужественный*) в наших примерах, приведенных выше, являются простыми синонимами.

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TYOLOGICAL SPECIFICITIES OF METAPHORICAL EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This study examines the typological features of metaphorical expressions in English and Uzbek, showing how the analytic nature of English and the agglutinative structure of Uzbek shape metaphor formation and interpretation. It explores the link between linguistic form and cognition, focusing on conceptual, cultural, and structural dimensions of metaphor. The comparative analysis demonstrates how each language reflects its worldview and provides insights that support translation, intercultural communication, and language teaching.

Keywords: *metaphor, typology, conceptual metaphor, metaphorical expressions, linguistic form.*

The research focuses on the typological specificities of metaphorical expressions in English and Uzbek. It highlights how the analytic nature of English and the agglutinative structure of Uzbek shape the formation and interpretation of metaphors. Metaphor, as both a cognitive and cultural phenomenon, reflects how speakers conceptualize reality and express values. In English, metaphors often arise through syntactic structures and idiomatic combinations, emphasizing clarity and fixed phraseology. Uzbek, by contrast, employs affixation, compounding, and semantic extension, enabling greater creativity and emotional depth. Cultural context is equally important: English metaphors reflect individualism, technology, and pragmatism, while Uzbek metaphors embody spirituality, collective values, and nature. By exploring these differences, the study reveals the interrelation between language typology, cognition, and worldview, contributing to translation accuracy, intercultural communication, and language teaching.

American scholars, particularly George Lakoff and Mark Johnson (1980) [3], laid the intellectual foundation for the modern study of conceptual metaphor through their influential work *“Metaphors We Live By.”* They proposed that metaphors are not simply figures of speech used for artistic or rhetorical purposes, but rather fundamental cognitive mechanisms that shape how humans perceive, think, and interact with the world. According to their theory, metaphors allow individuals to understand abstract concepts through more concrete, physical, and familiar experiences. Lakoff (1993) [4] later elaborated on this theory by identifying three main types of metaphors: conceptual metaphors, which map one domain of experience onto another (e.g., *argument is war*); orientational metaphors, which organize a whole system of concepts with respect to spatial orientation (e.g., *happy is up, sad is down*); and ontological metaphors, which give abstract concepts physical form (e.g., *the mind is a container*). These classifications helped scholars understand that everyday language is filled with metaphorical structures that reflect deeper mental frameworks. For instance, English expressions like *“time is money,” “spend time,” “waste time,”* and *“save time”* show how time, an abstract notion, is conceptualized as a valuable commodity in Western society. Similarly, the metaphor *“argument is war”* reveals how conflict-oriented reasoning and competitiveness are central to American discourse and communication styles. Following Lakoff and Johnson, other researchers such as Raymond Gibbs (1994) [1] and Zoltán Kövecses (2002) [2] expanded the study of metaphor by emphasizing its cultural and psychological dimensions. They argued that metaphors not only mirror human cognition but also express cultural values, social structures, and collective experiences. Kövecses highlighted that while conceptual metaphors are universal in nature, their specific linguistic realizations differ across cultures due to distinct worldviews and social norms. In the case of American English, metaphors often reflect values such as individualism, time efficiency, productivity, competition, and pragmatism, which are dominant features of Western culture. For example, the frequent use of metaphors like *“life is a race,” “business is a game,”* and *“knowledge is power”* shows how American speakers view life and success as measurable, goal-oriented, and competitive processes. Overall, American research on metaphor has shifted the focus from metaphor as mere decoration to metaphor as a key to understanding the human conceptual system and cultural mindset.

In contrast, Uzbek scholars such as A. Madvaliev (2008) [6], N. Mahmudov (2013) [5], and D. Tursunov (2016) [7] have explored metaphors from both typological and cultural-linguistic perspectives, showing how metaphor reflects the national spirit, worldview, and aesthetic traditions of the Uzbek people. Uzbek metaphors are deeply rooted in folklore, proverbs, poetry, and moral philosophy, reflecting emotional, spiritual, and ethical values. Expressions like *“ko‘ngil ko‘zi”* (eye of the heart) or *“ilm nuridir”* (knowledge is light) symbolize consciousness, morality, and attachment, showing metaphor’s didactic and ethical function. Unlike English, where metaphors emphasize rational control and functionality, Uzbek metaphors highlight harmony between mind, heart, and spirit, often enriched by personification and nature imagery. Scholars note that while Western metaphors center on efficiency and logic, Uzbek metaphors prioritize collective identity, moral beauty, and spirituality. This contrast demonstrates that metaphors, though universal, embody each nation’s cultural worldview and linguistic identity.

The comparison between American and Uzbek metaphorical systems reveals not only linguistic differences but also profound cultural contrasts in the way people perceive, conceptualize, and communicate reality. Although both languages use metaphors to express abstract ideas through concrete imagery, their underlying cognitive patterns and cultural associations differ significantly due to distinct historical, philosophical, and social

backgrounds. In American English, metaphors tend to be rational, functional, and goal-oriented, reflecting the influence of Western individualism and pragmatic philosophy. Phrases like “*time is money*,” “*life is a race*,” “*success is a journey*,” and “*knowledge is power*” embody a worldview where time, effort, and competition are seen as measurable and valuable commodities. These metaphors demonstrate that Americans often perceive life as a series of tasks or challenges that require control, discipline, and personal achievement. The language thus promotes a linear and progress-oriented concept of reality. In contrast, Uzbek metaphors are often emotionally expressive, spiritual, and collectivist, reflecting traditional values rooted in human relationships, respect, and harmony. Expressions such as “*ona zamin*” (“mother earth”), “*ko‘ngil ko‘zi*” (“the eye of the heart”), and “*ilm nuridir*” (“knowledge is light”) reveal a symbolic and moral understanding of the world. Uzbek metaphorical thinking emphasizes inner beauty, wisdom, kindness, and unity, where emotions and spirituality play a central role in communication. Rather than focusing on competition or material success, Uzbek metaphors convey balance, loyalty, and shared experience. Another key difference lies in conceptual domains. American metaphors are often derived from business, sports, and technology, illustrating an active, modern, and dynamic culture. Uzbek metaphors, on the other hand, are drawn from nature, family, and moral life, rooted in agrarian traditions and poetic heritage.

For instance, the English metaphor “*time flies*” portrays time as a fast-moving object, while the Uzbek equivalent “*vaqt suvdek oqadi*” (“time flows like water”) expresses the same concept but with natural and harmonious imagery, showing patience and acceptance rather than urgency. Furthermore, American metaphors frequently emphasize the individual’s control over external circumstances (“take control of your life”), whereas Uzbek metaphors highlight the interconnectedness of people and fate (“taqdir yozilgan,” meaning “destiny is written”). This suggests that English metaphors are more agentive and analytical, while Uzbek metaphors are more philosophical and relational.

Overall, both metaphorical systems demonstrate that language is a mirror of culture and thought. American metaphors project an image of a society that values independence, achievement, and time management, while Uzbek metaphors reflect a worldview centered on spirituality, morality, and human connection. Understanding these differences not only deepens linguistic knowledge but also fosters intercultural awareness and appreciation of how metaphor shapes the identity and mindset of each nation.

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E-LEARNING AND BLENDED LEARNING: LINGUISTIC AND PEDAGOGICAL PERSPECTIVES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the development of e-learning and blended learning models in Uzbekistan from both linguistic and pedagogical perspectives. It focuses on how digital technologies affect the process of language teaching and learning, particularly in developing communicative competence and learner autonomy. The paper discusses theoretical foundations, modern approaches, practical implementations, and challenges in the integration of e-learning and blended learning within the Uzbek education system. The authors conclude that digital learning environments, when combined with traditional classroom practices, offer an effective and innovative platform for improving the quality of language education in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: e-learning, blended learning, linguistics, pedagogy, Uzbekistan, digitalization, traditional, classroom, practical, development.

The 21st century has witnessed a digital revolution that significantly impacts education systems around the world. Modern technologies have changed the way people learn, communicate, and acquire knowledge. In this context, e-learning and blended learning have become essential tools in linguistics and pedagogy. They support the development of communicative competence, learner autonomy, and interactive teaching methods. In Uzbekistan, these approaches play an important role in modernizing the education system and improving the quality of language instruction. E-Learning in Modern Linguistics and Pedagogy. E-learning is a method of education that uses digital technologies, internet platforms, and multimedia resources to facilitate learning. According to Garrison and Anderson (2003), e-learning creates new opportunities for interactive and flexible education.

From a linguistic point of view, it provides students with access to authentic materials, online discussions, and pronunciation tools that improve their language skills. In pedagogy, e-learning helps teachers to organize virtual lessons, conduct assessments, and monitor student progress more effectively. In Uzbekistan, universities and schools use Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle, Google Classroom, and Edmodo to deliver online courses. These systems became especially important during the COVID-19 pandemic, ensuring continuity in the learning process.

Blended Learning as a New Educational Trend. Blended learning combines traditional face-to-face education with online learning. This model is considered one of the most effective approaches in modern pedagogy (Graham, 2006). In linguistics, blended learning helps students practice communication, reading, and writing both online and offline. For example, online platforms provide additional exercises and video materials, while classroom discussions help reinforce theoretical knowledge. Thus, blended learning encourages independent learning and collaborative interaction among students. Implementation and Experience in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has made significant progress in the field of digital education. The government has launched national programs aimed at integrating ICT into the education system.

Many universities have introduced digital libraries, e-assessment systems, and virtual laboratories. Language faculties are increasingly adopting e-learning for English and Uzbek

linguistics courses. However, several challenges still exist. These include uneven internet access, lack of digital content in the Uzbek language, and limited teacher training in ICT. To overcome these challenges, continuous professional development programs and infrastructure improvements are required.

E-learning and blended learning are transforming the linguistic and pedagogical landscape of Uzbekistan. They enhance the accessibility, flexibility, and quality of education while promoting digital literacy among students and teachers. Although there are still difficulties in implementation, ongoing reforms and investments in technology will ensure further development of digital education. In conclusion, the integration of e-learning and blended learning will strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the global educational environment and support the growth of innovative teaching practices.

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NEMIS TILI DIALEKTOLOGIYASI: ME'YORIY TIL VA LAHJAVIY SO'ZLASHUV QARAMA-QARSHILIGI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada nemis tili dialektologiyasi, ya'ni me'yoriy til (Hochdeutsch) va lahjaviy so'zlashuvlar o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshilik tahlil qilinadi. Germaniyada mavjud bo'lgan turli dialektlar va ularning fonetik, leksik hamda grammatik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Nemis tili, dialektologiya, me'yoriy til, lahja, fonetika, leksika, grammatik farqlar, tilshunoslik, sotsiolingvistika, ta'limdagi muammolar, madaniyat, dialektni saqlash

НЕМЕЦКАЯ ДИАЛЕКТОЛОГИЯ: ПРОТИВОПОСТАВЛЕНИЕ НОРМАТИВНОГО ЯЗЫКА И ДИАЛЕКТНОЙ РЕЧИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается диалектология немецкого языка, а именно противоречие между нормативным языком (Hochdeutsch) и диалектным говором. Анализируются различные диалекты, существующие в Германии, их фонетические, лексические и грамматические особенности.

Ключевые слова: Немецкий язык, диалектология, нормативный язык, диалект, фонетика, лексика, грамматические различия, лингвистика, социолингвистика, проблемы в образовании, культура, сохранение диалектов.

GERMAN DIALECTOLOGY: THE OPPOSITION BETWEEN STANDARD LANGUAGE AND DIALECTAL SPEECH

Abstract. This article explores German dialectology, focusing on the contrast between the standard language (Hochdeutsch) and regional dialects. It examines the various dialects present in Germany, highlighting their phonetic, lexical, and grammatical features.

Keywords: German language, dialectology, standard language, dialect, phonetics, lexicon, grammatical differences, linguistics, sociolinguistics, educational challenges, culture, dialect preservation.

Nemis tili dunyodagi eng ko'p o'rganilayotgan tillardan biri bo'lib, uning murakkabliklaridan biri bu – dialektlar xilma-xilligi hisoblanadi. Germaniyada har bir hududda deyarli o'ziga xos lahjaviy so'zlashuv mavjud bo'lib, ular orasida fonetik, leksik, morfologik va sintaktik farqlar chuqur ildiz otgan. Bu holat tilshunoslikda dialektologiya deb ataluvchi soha doirasida o'rganiladi. Ushbu maqolada nemis tili dialektlarining umumiy xususiyatlari, me'yoriy til bilan qarama-qarshiligi, shuningdek, bu qarama-qarshilikning tilshunoslik va ijtimoiy hayotdagi ta'siri yoritiladi. Nemis tilining dialektlari qadimiy german tillaridan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, 8–11-asrlarda mavjud bo'lgan “Old High German” (OHG) shakllaridan rivojlangan. 16-asrda Martin Lyuter Injilni turli dialektlar o'rtasida nisbatan tushunarli bo'lgan Meissner (Saksoniya) lahjasi asosida tarjima qilgan. Bu esa hozirgi standart nemis tilining, ya'ni Hochdeutschning poydevorini yaratdi. Germaniyada dialektlar uchta asosiy guruhga bo'linadi: yuqori nemis dialektlari (Oberdeutsch), o'rta nemis dialektlari (Mitteldeutsch) va quyi nemis dialektlari (Niederdeutsch). Yuqori nemis dialektlari janubiy Germaniya, Avstriya va Shvetsariya hududlarida keng tarqalgan bo'lib, Bavariya, Shvabiya va Avstriya lahjalari shular jumlasidandir. O'rta nemis dialektlari esa Frankfurt va Drezden atrofida uchraydi. Quyi nemis dialektlari esa Shimoliy Germaniyada, xususan Bremen va Hamburg hududlarida keng tarqalgan. Ushbu dialektlar o'zaro fonetik, leksik, grammatik jihatdan sezilarli farqlarga ega bo'lib, ba'zan bir 167ialect so'zlashuvchisi boshqa 167ialect so'zlashuvchisini tushunmay qoladi. Bugungi kunda Germaniyada standart til sifatida qabul qilingan Hochdeutsch asosan yozma til asosida shakllangan bo'lib, rasmiy muomalada, ta'limda, ommaviy axborot vositalarida va ilmiy sohada keng qo'llaniladi. Martin Lyuter tarjimasi natijasida shakllangan ushbu standart til o'zaro muloqotni osonlashtiradi va jamiyatni birlashtiruvchi vosita hisoblanadi. Biroq, xalq orasida, ayniqsa qishloq joylarda va janubiy hududlarda dialektlar faol qo'llaniladi. Tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan, dialektlar tilning jonli, hududiy va madaniy jihatdan boy shakllarini ifodalaydi. Me'yoriy til esa tilning 167ialect167c va universal shaklidir. Biroq, me'yoriy til rivojlanib, lingvistik unifikatsiyaga xizmat qilgan sari dialektlar asta-sekin chekinmoqda. Bu jarayon tilshunoslar tomonidan “lingvistik assilyatsiya” deb ataladi. Ijtimoiy nuqtai nazardan qaraganda esa, dialektda so'zlashuvchilar ko'pincha madaniy jihatdan kamroq rivojlangan yoki 167ialect167c167 deb noto'g'ri baholanadi. Bu esa ijtimoiy tafovutlarga, kamsitishga olib kelishi mumkin. Ta'lim tizimida esa bolalar uyda dialektda so'zlashib ulg'aygan bo'lsa, maktabda standart tilga moslashishda qiyinchiliklar yuzaga keladi. Bu esa 167ialect167c va tilshunoslik masalalarini yuzaga chiqaradi.

Nemis dialektlari talaffuz (fonetik), so'z boyligi (leksik) va grammatik jihatdan turlicha bo'ladi. Masalan, “kichkina qiz” ifodasi standart nemis tilida “das kleine Mädchen”

bo'lsa, Bavariya dialektida "s kloane Madl", Shimoliy dialektida (Plattdeutsch) esa "dat lütte Deern" shaklida ifodalanadi. Shuningdek, ayrim dialektlarda ayrim so'zlar butunlay boshqacha talaffuz qilinadi yoki boshqa ma'noga ega bo'ladi. Dialektologiyada strukturalizm nazariyasi tilni tizimli birliklar majmui sifatida o'rganadi va dialektlarni tilning ichki o'zgarishlari sifatida qabul qiladi. Sotsiolingvistika esa dialektlarni ijtimoiy identifikatsiya vositasi sifatida ko'radi va ularning jamiyatdagi o'rnini tadqiq qiladi. Masalan, ingliz tilshunosi Uilyam Labovning tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, til va lahja ijtimoiy maqomni ko'rsatadi; me'yoriy til yuqori ijtimoiy qatlam vakillari tomonidan qo'llaniladi, 168 dialect esa ko'proq mahalliy va kamroq rasmiy qatlamlarda. Germaniyada ta'limda faqat me'yoriy til o'rgatiladi. Bu holatda uyda dialektida so'zlashib ulg'aygan bolalar uchun o'qishda qiynchiliklar yuzaga keladi. Bunday holatlar "diglossiya" deb ataladi – jamiyatda ikkita til shakli mavjud bo'lib, biri rasmiy kontekstda, ikkinchisi esa kundalik hayotda ishlatiladi. Masalan, Shveysariyada bolalar uyda "Schweizerdeutsch" dialektida gaplashadi, maktabda esa Hochdeutschni o'rganadi.

Dialektlar milliy madaniyatning ajralmas qismi sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Ayrim hududiy hukumatlar dialektlarni saqlash va rivojlantirish maqsadida maxsus qonunlar va dasturlar ishlab chiqqan. Shuningdek, 2006-yilda UNESCO tomonidan ayrim nemis dialektlari, xususan Plattdeutsch, yo'qolish xavfi ostidagi tillar sifatida qayd etilgan. Shu sababli, dialektlarni madaniy meros sifatida saqlash muhim vazifa hisoblanadi. Dialektologlar turli usullardan foydalanadilar. Hududlarda so'zlashuvlarni xaritaga tushirish, maydonda intervyular olish, talaffuz farqlarini laboratoriya sharoitida o'rganish kabi metodlar keng qo'llaniladi. Bu tadqiqotlar natijalari dialektlarning geografik va lingvistik chegaralarini aniqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Germaniyada aholining taxminan 30–35% har kuni dialektida so'zlashadi, 70–80% esa dialektni tushunadi. Rasmiy hujjatlar, ta'lim va ommaviy axborot vositalarida esa asosan Hochdeutsch ishlatiladi. Eng faol 168 dialect zonalari janubiy Germaniya, Baden-Vyurtemberg, Saksoniya, Shveysariya va Avstriya hududlari hisoblanadi. Germaniyada me'yoriy til va dialektlar o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshilik nafaqat tilshunoslik, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy muammo sifatida ham ko'riladi. Me'yoriy til jamiyatni birlashtiruvchi vosita bo'lsa, dialektlar esa milliy madaniyatning qadimiy ildizlari hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun, dialektlarni saqlash va hurmat qilish bilan birga, me'yoriy tilni rivojlantirish ham muhimdir. Germaniyaning bu boradagi tajribasi boshqa ko'plab tillar va ko'ptilli jamiyatlar uchun ham ibrat bo'la oladi.

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LINGUO-CULTURAL ASPECTS OF ABSTRACT NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract: In order to demonstrate how morphological development, semantic domains, and cultural salience influence the lexicalization of intangible concepts in both languages, this research compares the linguo-cultural characteristics of abstract nouns in Uzbek and English. The study emphasizes variations in derivational strategies (e.g., Uzbek suffixes -lik, -chilik vs. English -ness, -ity, -hood), metaphorical extensions, and pragmatic usage linked to social values like honor, family, and community. It does this by drawing on contrastive analysis, a few chosen corpus examples, and cross-linguistic literature. According to the results, cultural goals and grammatical resources result in different lexical profiles and translation difficulties even if both languages employ similar cognitive processes to convey abstraction. There includes discussion of the implications for intercultural communication, language instruction, and translation studies.

Key words: abstract nouns, Uzbek, English, linguistic culture, nominalization, contrastive analysis, lexicalization.

Abstract nouns lexical items referring to intangible phenomena such as emotions, states, qualities, and social constructs are central to how languages encode human experience. They stand at the intersection of language and culture because the selection, frequency, and connotations of abstract terms reflect cultural priorities, conceptual metaphors, and social organization. This paper contrasts the expression of abstract concepts in Uzbek, a Turkic agglutinative language with a strong system of suffixal nominalization, and English, a Germanic analytic language that relies on a variety of derivational suffixes and compounding strategies. The goal is to identify linguo-cultural patterns that affect formation, meaning, and use of abstract nouns, and to point out challenges for translation and pedagogy. Cross-linguistic research on nominalization and cultural conceptualization has emphasized that languages differ not only in morphological means but also in what they lexicalize as stable concepts (Sapir, 1921; Whorf, 1956; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Turkic languages, including Uzbek, have been studied for rich agglutinative morphology and affixation strategies that produce abstract nouns (Johanson, 1998; Johanson & Csató, 1998). Studies in English morphology highlight frequent use of Latinate and Germanic suffixes (-ity, -ness, -tion, -hood) and the role of borrowings in expanding abstract vocabulary (Bauer, 2003). Contrastive and translation-oriented studies point to frequent non-equivalence in lexicalized abstractions, which requires explicitation or paraphrase in translation (Newmark, 1988; Vinay & Darbelnet, 1995).

The study employs a qualitative contrastive approach to analyze how abstract nouns in Uzbek and English are formed, conceptualized, and culturally framed. This approach draws on three primary components: Morphological comparison of the most common derivational suffixes used to form abstract nouns; Semantic field sampling, which focuses on key domains such as emotions, moral qualities, social relations, and epistemic states; and Illustrative examples drawn from bilingual dictionaries, literary and journalistic translations, and small web corpora to show contextual and pragmatic differences.

Through this methodology, the research seeks to demonstrate how linguistic structure and cultural cognition interact to shape abstract thought and expression in two distinct

linguistic systems. Uzbek is typologically agglutinative, meaning that words are formed through the linear addition of suffixes, each carrying a distinct grammatical or semantic function. Verbs and adjectives can easily take on nominalizing suffixes to form abstract nouns. Among the most productive suffixes are:

-lik / -lik – denoting quality, condition, or state (e.g., do‘stlik ‘friendship’, go‘zallik ‘beauty’, ozodlik ‘freedom’).

-chilik – indicating occupation, collective activity, or social practice (e.g., dehqonchilik ‘farming’, o‘qituvchilik ‘teaching’, sotuvchilik ‘trading’).

-uv / -ish – functioning as action nouns derived from verbs, often used to denote processes or continuous activities (yozish ‘writing’, o‘qish ‘reading/study’).

-ot / -on – less productive but still significant in certain dialectal or formal registers (insoniyat ‘humanity’, do‘stlik ‘friendship’). These morphological tools allow Uzbek speakers to easily create new abstract nouns with transparent meanings. Additionally, Persian and Arabic loanwords enrich Uzbek’s abstract lexicon, particularly in religious, moral, and philosophical domains (e.g., ma’naviyat ‘spirituality’, adolat ‘justice’, iman ‘faith’, ta’lim ‘education’). The presence of these borrowings illustrates how historical and cultural contact shaped the Uzbek conceptual world.

In contrast, English, being a morphologically mixed and largely analytic language, uses several derivational strategies to form abstract nouns. Common suffixes include:

-ness (happiness, darkness, politeness) - typically derived from adjectives;

-ity / -ty / -cy (curiosity, sensitivity, privacy) - derived from Latinate roots;

-tion / -sion (creation, decision, conclusion) - derived from verbs of Latin origin;

-hood / -ship / -dom (childhood, friendship, freedom) - of Germanic origin, expressing states or relationships.

Additionally, English employs zero-derivation (e.g., to love → love, to hope → hope) and compounding (motherhood, leadership) as productive nominalization methods. Due to its hybrid Germanic-Latinate vocabulary, English demonstrates strong register differentiation: Latinate-derived abstractions often belong to formal, academic, or bureaucratic discourse, while Germanic forms are more common in everyday speech.

Both Uzbek and English employ shared cognitive and linguistic mechanisms for abstract conceptualization but diverge in morphological structure and cultural orientation. Uzbek’s agglutinative system and its integration of Persian-Arabic moral lexicon give rise to socially embedded and collectivist abstractions. English, shaped by its mixed derivational heritage and historical processes of secularization and individualization, foregrounds personal autonomy and analytical precision.

Recognizing these linguo-cultural dynamics enriches translation practice, enhances language pedagogy, and fosters deeper intercultural understanding. Abstract nouns, though often overlooked, represent the core of cultural cognition the linguistic bridge between thought, emotion, and societal value.

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LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH NEWSPAPER ADVERTISEMENTS: A MODERN LINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: This article explores the linguistic and stylistic features of English newspaper advertisements from a modern linguistic perspective. Newspaper advertising is a special form of media discourse that combines informative, persuasive, and aesthetic functions. The study identifies lexical, syntactic, and stylistic devices used to attract readers' attention and to influence their choices. Linguistic features such as lexical innovation, syntactic compression, emotional vocabulary, and imperative constructions are examined. Stylistically, the analysis focuses on metaphor, personification, and sound patterns that increase memorability. The study also addresses how digitalization affects the linguistic structure of newspaper advertisements, emphasizing the continuity of persuasive strategies across media forms.

Keywords: newspaper discourse, advertising language, stylistic devices, media linguistics, persuasion, lexical features, syntax, metaphor, communication, modern trends.

Advertising is one of the most dynamic and creative areas of linguistic practice. As part of newspaper discourse, it reflects the cultural and social values of a given society while fulfilling both economic and communicative functions. The English newspaper advertisement is a hybrid text type that integrates elements of journalistic, colloquial, and literary styles. It aims not only to inform readers about products and services but also to persuade and emotionally engage them.

The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the linguistic and stylistic features of English newspaper advertisements, emphasizing how they function in modern communicative contexts. The relevance of the research lies in the growing importance of understanding persuasive discourse in the media age and the need to develop linguistic awareness among readers and consumers.

1. Linguistic Features of Newspaper Advertisements. Linguistically, newspaper advertisements are distinguished by brevity, expressiveness, and emotional impact. The limited space in print media encourages advertisers to use language economically, ensuring that every word contributes to the overall persuasive effect.

1.1. Lexical Features. The vocabulary of advertising is dominated by positively charged adjectives such as *fresh*, *smart*, *clean*, and *bright*, which evoke desirable associations [1, p. 45]. Superlative and comparative forms (*better*, *best*, *ultimate*) serve to position a product above its competitors. Neologisms and brand-specific terms like *PowerClean* or *EcoBoost* introduce innovation and individuality, reinforcing the uniqueness of the advertised item.

Emotive and connotative vocabulary plays a vital role in forming a positive image of the product. For example, terms such as *luxury*, *comfort*, and *freedom* evoke abstract ideals that go beyond the product's physical properties. Neologisms and brand-specific terms (*PowerClean*, *SmartFit*, *EcoDrive*) demonstrate the creativity of advertisers and serve to make products linguistically distinctive.

Colloquial and idiomatic expressions (*Grab it now! Don't miss out!*) create a sense of immediacy and familiarity, reducing the psychological distance between advertiser and reader. The language often adopts the tone of everyday conversation, helping to establish trust and emotional connection.

1.2. Syntactic Features. Syntactically, newspaper advertisements favor simplicity and clarity. Sentences are often short and easily processed by the reader. Imperative structures (*Buy now! Try it today!*) are common, functioning as direct calls to action [2, p. 78]. Parallelism and repetition enhance rhythm and memorability: "*Better taste. Better life.*" Such patterns create a sense of harmony and reinforce the central message.

Parallelism and repetition are used to reinforce rhythm and memorability: "*Better design. Better quality. Better you.*" These structures rely on linguistic symmetry to achieve persuasive emphasis, transforming language into a rhythmic pattern that resonates with the audience.

1.3. Pragmatic and Semantic Aspects. Advertising texts rely heavily on pragmatic factors - the shared knowledge, cultural norms, and expectations of the audience. For instance, the slogan "*Because you're worth it*" presupposes an awareness of self-value and social aspiration. Ambiguity, irony, and wordplay are often used to stimulate interpretation and engagement. The pragmatic approach to meaning thus emphasizes the reader's active role in decoding and co-constructing the message.

2. Stylistic Devices in Advertising Discourse. Stylistic analysis reveals the aesthetic and emotional layers of advertising language. Advertisers manipulate form, sound, and imagery to heighten appeal and memorability.

2.1. Figurative Language. Figurative language constitutes one of the central tools of advertising style. Metaphors, personifications, and hyperboles are used to enrich the text with vivid imagery and emotional nuance. Expressions such as "*Taste the feeling*" (Coca-Cola) or "*Your skin loves Nivea*" personalize products and establish emotional bonds between the consumer and the brand [3, p. 112]. Hyperbolic claims like "*The best coffee in the universe*" exaggerate reality but reinforce memorability and product prestige.

2.2. Sound and Rhythm. Phonetic devices - including alliteration, assonance, and rhyme - are widely used to enhance sound symbolism and rhythm. Examples such as "*Coca-Cola - cool, crisp, classic*" demonstrate how repetition of initial consonants and vowel harmony create a melodious effect that aids recall [4, p. 63]. The euphonic quality of such slogans ensures that they resonate with the audience long after reading.

2.3. Graphic and Visual Stylistics. Typography and layout are integral to the stylistic structure of newspaper advertisements. The use of capital letters, bold fonts, and strategic spacing draws attention to key elements such as *NEW*, *FREE*, or *NOW*. Modern newspaper design increasingly combines visual and textual elements, integrating color, images, and symbols to amplify meaning. The interplay of verbal and visual cues enhances emotional impact and strengthens the overall communicative intention.

3. Transformation of Advertising in the Digital Era. With the rise of digital technologies, the boundaries between traditional newspaper and online advertising have become increasingly blurred. Many print newspapers now maintain digital versions, incorporating hyperlinks, hashtags, and interactive graphics [5, p. 24]. Although the medium has evolved, the fundamental linguistic strategies - brevity, emotional appeal, and stylistic creativity - remain central to persuasive communication.

While digital advertisements often adopt a more conversational and personalized tone ("*Your perfect look is one click away!*"), they still rely on the same persuasive linguistic devices that characterized traditional print ads. The immediacy of online communication

encourages informality, while hyperlinking and hashtags create a sense of participation and connectivity.

4. Cultural and Sociolinguistic Aspects. English newspaper advertisements mirror the cultural values of modern society - individuality, progress, and self-realization. Slogans such as “*Be yourself*” or “*Think different*” highlight Western ideals of autonomy and creativity [6, p. 87]. The language of advertising thus becomes a reflection of social aspirations and collective identity.

Cross-cultural studies indicate that English-language advertisements adapted for non-English-speaking contexts often retain their stylistic and emotional core, demonstrating the global influence of English as a language of prestige and innovation. Advertising, therefore, functions as both a linguistic and sociocultural phenomenon, shaping and reflecting contemporary worldviews.

Conclusion. English newspaper advertisements demonstrate a complex balance between linguistic economy and stylistic expressiveness. Through careful selection of lexical items, syntactic structures, and stylistic devices, advertisers achieve clarity, memorability, and persuasive power. The transition from print to digital formats has expanded the communicative possibilities of advertising discourse but has preserved its essential linguistic mechanisms - creativity, brevity, and emotional engagement.

A comprehensive linguistic and stylistic study of advertisements contributes not only to the field of media linguistics but also to the development of media literacy and critical awareness in modern education. Understanding how language constructs meaning in persuasive contexts enables readers to navigate contemporary media more consciously and effectively.

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VERBALIZATION OF BRITISH HUMOR AS A CULTURAL CODE

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Annotation: This research explores how British humor in modern satirical journalism functions as a linguocultural code reflecting social tensions and national values. Using rhetorical and pragmatic analysis of Marina Hyde's and Giles Coren's newspaper columns, it examines parody, dark humor, and self-deprecation as key strategies of indirect criticism and politeness. Humor transforms frustration and political irony into a shared cultural reflection, preserving the norms of restraint and understatement typical of British communication.

Keywords: linguocultural code, British humor, dark humor, self-deprecation, negative politeness, social distinction, rhetoric, political satire, journalistic discourse

Humor as a Linguocultural Code. By examining humor from the fields of philology and language pedagogy, and attempting to explore cultural notions from various perspectives, people hope to collect useful evidence of cultural thought patterns. Humor is fundamentally contextual and collaborative; it operates like a grand banquet that we all partake in together. Within national characters, humour refers to a lot lingua-cultura, including particular symbols through non-verbal means, and expressions from value cultures and communication habits. British humor is certainly crazy, and restraint, but together just doesn't compute [10, p. 158]. This code is also used strategically in modern public speech To combat the trend of people taking themselves entirely too seriously, humour can be exploited as either an individual defense or as a weapon. The British preference for being indirect and an ability to maintain social distance limits any direct criticism of others [11, p. 313]. Humour therefore becomes a sociopragmatic tool for addressing Society 's various frustrations as well as deeply rooted problems, but: Well, with its more delicate handling can be so arranged- The sort that doesn't offend and is socially acceptable. This conscious use of irony and comic ethos still served in daily life to carve out for oneself some cash or respect is one of the essential characteristics of UK communicative identity today.

To illustrate how British humour functions as a linguocultural code when reported in the press, analysis will use two works of satirical journalism: Giles Coren's 'Seven hours of train hell stops me going north' [4] and Marina Hyde's 'Mirror, mirror on the wall, who is the biggest patriot of them all? It is I, Robert Jenrick' [7]. Both authors use irony, self-mockery and cultural commentary to communicate national dissatisfaction - while also preserving the beloved British reserve.

Self-Deprecation and Structural Contrast. Self-deprecation (SD) is commonly employed as a rhetorical calibration in both social and journalistic discourse for purposes of warding off charges of arrogance or hyper-complaining. Coren's column converts a mundane travel hell into something more reflective of the society at large.

Coren describes his seven-hour trip home, quizzing a guard on the consequences of trying to catch an earlier train without paying: "What about prison? I asked. Would I also go to prison?" [4]. COMEDY here comes from this exaggerated self-deprecation and the juxtaposition between small personal suffering, incompetence, with society's ills.

He compares his own travel misery to a real tragedy (someone dying on the line) but insists that this level of hassle, visited to thousands across Britain every day, for decade after decade, is itself a national disaster [4]. As such, his turn demonstrates Speer's theory of self-deprecating talk as a form of interactional trouble talking and rhetorical tool for getting out of "interactional trouble" [9, p. 806]. The restrained ending constitutes negative politeness, and is a way of converting an individual complaint into a mode of cultural self-identification.

Lampoons, Black Humor and Other Uses of Satire. Satirical columns of today adopt sarcasm to spoof political haughtiness and self-centeredness. In Hyde's column, persona satire is deployed here to create an exaggerated interior monologue for a politician, Robert Jenrick: "Mirror, mirror on the wall, who is the biggest patriot of them all? It is I, Robert Jenrick" [7]. The "culture war" is a sign of that, when national values become petty symbols.

When a political cartoon is humorous they are overwhelmingly effective, combining satire with dark humor. Hyde's satire reveals the nationalist masquerade, that it is "all just a ridiculous charade"-as the politician admires himself thinking: "Run me up the flagpole and see who salutes me" [7].

Another example of dark comedy comes as the team tries to outflank a political opponent on immigration: "You could," a third says, "come up with an even tougher, catchier name for the internment camps." "Like what?" I snap. But they're all looking at their shoes.

That's what is wrong with this generation - f- all attention span." [8]. This subversive irony serves as an insurgent critique [3, p. 40] and is consistent with Friedman's perspective of humor as culture capital [5, p. 347; 7].

Conclusion. The article shows that British humor today has not abandoned its classic social uses of restraint, irony, and self-deprecation but applies them to the politics of new journalism. Both Coren and Hyde employ the comic as a sociopragmatic apparatus, displacing anger and ideology with polite reflective critique. In this way they demonstrate that humour is inherently double, a communicative convention and a cultural ideogram, the one which through laughter still jeopardizes and articulates the British world order.

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INKOR KATEGORIYASI VA UNING LINGVISTIK HUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada inkor kategoriyasining lingvistik xususiyatlari, uning ifoda vositalari va turli tillarda namoyon bo‘lish shakllari tahlil qilinadi. Inkorning grammatik va semantik jihatlari, shuningdek, uning sintaktik tuzilmalardagi o‘rni yoritiladi. Turli tillardagi inkor shakllarining qiyosiy tahlili orqali umumiy va o‘ziga xos xususiyatlar aniqlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: inkor, inkor kategoriyasi, lingvistika, grammatik vosita, semantika, sintaksis, qiyosiy tahlil

Annotation: This article analyzes the linguistic features of the negation category, its means of expression, and how it is manifested in different languages. The grammatical and semantic aspects of negation, as well as its role in syntactic structures, are explored. A

comparative analysis of negation forms in various languages helps to identify both universal and language-specific features.

Keywords: negation, category of negation, linguistics, grammatical means, semantics, syntax, comparative analysis

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются лингвистические особенности категории отрицания, средства её выражения и формы проявления в разных языках. Освещаются грамматические и семантические аспекты отрицания, а также его роль в синтаксических структурах. Сравнительный анализ форм отрицания в различных языках позволяет выявить как универсальные, так и специфические особенности.

Ключевые слова: отрицание, категория отрицания, лингвистика, грамматические средства, семантика, синтаксис, сравнительный анализ.

Inson tilini ichki mexanizimini ishlash printsiplarini o'rganish va tilning faoliyatini ta'minlab beradigan turli hodisalar va jarayonlarini o'rganish va tahlil qilis nazariy tilshunoslikning eng dolzarb muammosi bo'lgan va shunday bo'lib qoladi, chunki til statik emas, balki dinamik hodisadir.[1,5]

Hozirgi kunda xorijiy tillarini o'rganish va o'rgatish masalasi jamiyatimiz oldida turgan dolzarb vazifalardan biridir. Xorijiy tillarni ilmiy va amaliy o'rganishda qiyosiy-tipologik yondoshish, turli til sistemasiga mansub bo'lgan tillarni qiyoslab o'rganish, tillarning o'xshash va farqli qirralarini ochib berish nihoyatda samaradorli yondoshish hisoblanadi.

Tilshunoslikda inkor kategoriyasini turli tillar (materialida) o'rganishga qat'iy ahamiyat berilmoqda, chunki turli tillarda inkorlikni ifodalaydigan vositalar turlichadir.

Inkorlik kategoriyasini o'rganish jarayonida «*assimetriya*» hodisasini inobatga olish maksadga muvofiqdir, chunki assimetriya atamasi yunon tilida «*tilni tuzilshi va qo'llanilishi jarayonida vujudga keladigan tartibsizliklar*», ifodalovchi va ifodalanmish o'rtasida paydo bo'ladigan mos kelmasliklarni aniqlash va o'rganish ma'nosini anglatadi.

Masalan gapning grammatik strukturasi bilan mazmun strukturasi mos kelmasligi, tilshunoslikda «*gapni aktual bo'laklarga ajratish*» nazariyasini yaratilishiga sabab bo'ldi.

Gapni kommunikativ vazifasini nuqtai nazaridan jumlaning tashkil etuvchi elementlar «*tema*» (*ma'lum*) va «*rema*» (*yangi qisimlarga bo'linadi*). Gapning «*rema*» kismi eng ahamiyatli qism - *kommunikativ markaz* hisoblanadi.

Hozirgi tilshunoslikda inkorlikni o'rganishda mononegativlik va *polinegativlik* atamalar keng qo'llanilmoqda.

Shuni inobatga olish kerak-ki, inkorlik kategoriyasini ifodalashda til tizimini tashkil etgan barcha satxlar ishtirok etadi, inkorni ifodalovchi til vositalarni qiyosiy-tipologik tahlilida tarjimashunoslik ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI

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Anotatsiya: Hozirgi globallashuv va raqamli texnologiyalar asrida tilshunoslik fanining o'zni va ahamiyati tobora ortib bormoqda. Til insoniyatning asosiy aloqa vositasi, milliy o'zlik va madaniyatning ajralmas qismidir. Shu sababli tilshunoslik nafaqat tilning ichki tuzilishini, balki uning jamiyat, tafakkur, madaniyat va texnologiya bilan o'zaro aloqasini ham chuqur o'rganadi. So'nggi yillarda til tizimidagi o'zgarishlar, yangi axborot texnologiyalarining ta'siri, tillarning yo'qolib borishi, tarjima va nutq madaniyati bilan bog'liq masalalar tilshunoslik oldida yangi ilmiy vazifalarni qo'yimoqda.

Kalit So'zlar: Tilshunoslik, aloqa vositalari, jamiyat, tafakkur, madaniyat, texnologiya, grammatik kompetensiya, kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi, biling shaxslar.

Abstract: In the present era of globalization and digital technologies, the role and importance of linguistics are steadily increasing. Language is the main means of human communication, as well as an integral part of national identity and culture. Therefore, linguistics studies not only the internal structure of language, but also its deep interconnection with society, thinking, culture, and technology. In recent years, changes in the language system, the influence of new information technologies, the disappearance of languages, and issues related to translation and speech culture have

Key words: Linguistics, means of communication, society, thinking, culture, technology, grammatical competence, computer linguistics, corpus linguistics, bilingual individuals.

Tilshunoslikning keng tarqalgan muammolarini o'rganish - bu til taraqqiyotining hozirgi bosqichini tahlil qilish, duch kelgan muammolarga yechim topish va milliy tilning nufuzini yanada mustahkamlash uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu uchun ushbu maqolada zamonaviy tilshunoslikning asosiy dolzarb yo'nalishlari va ularning ilmiy ahamiyati yoritiladi.

Tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolarini o'rganishda mahalliy va xorijiy olimlarning ilmiy izlanishlari muhim o'rin tutadi. Tilning ijtimoiy, madaniy va psixologik mohiyatini tahlil qilishda N. Xomskiy, F. de Sossyur, E. Sapir, B. Uorf kabi tilshunoslarning asarlari asosiy nazariy manba sifatida xizmat qiladi. F. de Sossyur tilni ijtimoiy hodisa deb qarab, uni nutqdan farqlagan bo'lsa, N. Xomskiy tilning ichki tuzilishi, grammatik kompetensiya va inson tafakkuri bilan bog'liqligini tahlil qilgan.

O'zbek tilshunosligida esa N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, M. Jo'rayev, Sh. Safarov kabi olimlar tilning jamiyatdagi o'zni, normativ masalalar, nutq madaniyati hamda ikki tillilik

muammolarini keng o'rganib kelmoqda. Xususan, A. Nurmonov o'zbek tili sintaksisida mantiqiy va kommunikativ jihatlarning uyg'unligini tahlil qilgan bo'lsa, N. Mahmudov va A. Madvaliyevlar zamonaviy o'zbek tilining rivojlanish istiqbollari va yangi til birliklarining shakllanishi haqida ilmiy qarashlar bildirganlar.

So'nggi yillarda kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi, kognitiv tilshunoslik kabi yangi yo'nalishlarning paydo bo'lishi tilshunoslikda yangicha yondashuvlarni shakllantirmoqda. Masalan, E. Kubryakova va D. Crystal asarlarida tilni sun'iy intellekt tizimlariga tatbiq etish masalalari, til o'rganishda texnologiyaning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Shu bilan birga, internet tilshunosligi va sotsiolingvistika yo'nalishidagi izlanishlar tildagi zamonaviy o'zgarishlarni aniqlashga xizmat qilmoqda.

Umuman olganda, ilmiy adabiyotlarda tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari ko'p qirrali yondashuvlar asosida o'rganilmoqda: tilning ijtimoiy mohiyati, globalizatsiya sharoitida tillarning saqlanishi, nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish hamda texnologiyalar bilan uyg'unlashuvi zamonaviy tadqiqotlarning markazida turibdi. Hozirgi davrda tilshunoslik fanida bir qator dolzarb muammolar mavjud bo'lib, ular ilmiy tadqiqotlar markazida turadi.

Birinchi, globalizatsiya va ommaviy madaniyat ta'sirida ko'plab milliy tillar o'z mavqeini yo'qotish xavfi ostida qolmoqda. Ingliz tilining xalqaro miqyosda keng qo'llanilishi natijasida kichik xalqlar tillari asta-sekin faol nutqdan siqib chiqmoqda, bu esa lingvistik xilma-xillikka jiddiy tahdid tug'diradi.

Ikkinchi, raqamli texnologiyalar va internet tarmog'ining tez rivojlanishi til tizimida yangi so'z va iboralar, qisqartmalar, shuningdek, tilning normativ qoidalaridan chetlanish holatlarini kuchaytirmoqda. Bu esa adabiy til me'yorlarini saqlash va nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish masalasini murakkablashtirmoqda.

Uchinchi, ko'p tillilik va ikki tillilik jarayonlari tufayli tillar orasidagi aralashuv, ya'ni interferensiya kuchaymoqda. Bilingv shaxslar nutqida grammatik, leksik va fonetik xatoliklarning ko'payishi tilning tabiiy tuzilishiga ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda hamda ona tilning sof shaklini saqlashda muammolar keltirib chiqarmoqda.

Birinchi muammo - milliy tillarning yo'qolish xavfi. Bu muammoni bartaraf etish uchun, avvalo, har bir millat o'z tiliga nisbatan hurmat va mas'uliyatni oshirishi lozim. Davlat miqyosida milliy tilni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan dasturlarni kengaytirish, o'quv muassasalarida tilni chuqur o'qitish hamda ommaviy axborot vositalarida milliy tildagi kontentni ko'paytirish zarur. Shu bilan birga, yosh avlodda o'z ona tiliga muhabbatni kuchaytirish maqsadida adabiyot, teatr va madaniy tadbirlar orqali targ'ibot olib borish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ikkinchi muammo - texnologiyalar ta'sirida til me'yorlarining buzilishi. Bu holatning oldini olish uchun raqamli platformalarda adabiy til me'yorlarini qo'llash madaniyatini shakllantirish kerak. Internet lug'atlari, til grammatikasi uchun mobil ilovalar va avtomatik tahrir dasturlarini yaratish orqali foydalanuvchilarga to'g'ri yozish va gapirishni o'rgatish mumkin. Shuningdek, tilshunos olimlar va texnolog mutaxassislari hamkorligida elektron korpuslar, onlayn lug'atlar va avtomatik tarjima tizimlarini takomillashtirish lozim.

Uchinchi muammo - ikki tillilik natijasida interferensiya kuchayishi. Bu jarayonni nazorat qilish uchun til o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish muhim. Ona tili va chet tili o'qituvchilari birgalikda o'quvchilarda har ikki tilni to'g'ri qo'llash ko'nikmasini shakllantirishi kerak. Shuningdek, televizion dasturlar, radio eshittirishlar va internetdagi kontentlarda ona tilning sof shaklini targ'ib etish, til xatolarini ommaviy darajada tuzatish madaniyatini rivojlantirish samarali natija beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, tilshunoslik bugungi kunda insoniyat taraqqiyoti bilan chambarchas bog'liq fan sifatida yangi bosqichga ko'tarildi. Globalizatsiya, texnologiyalar

rivoji va madaniyatlararo muloqotning kengayishi natijasida til tizimida ko‘plab o‘zgarishlar yuz bermoqda. Bu esa milliy tillarning saqlanishi, adabiy me‘yorlarning barqarorligi va ikki tillilik muammolarini yanada dolzarb masalaga aylantirmoqda. Tilshunoslikning asosiy vazifasi - bu muammolarga ilmiy asosda yondashish, tilning tabiiy rivojlanish qonuniyatlarini saqlab qolish hamda uni yangi sharoitlarga moslashtirishdan iborat hisoblanadi. Har bir inson o‘z tiliga e’tibor bilan qarab, uni to‘g‘ri qo‘llashni o‘rganar ekan, til na ham aloqa vositasi, balki millatning ma’naviy boyligi sifatida e’zozlanadi. Shunday qilib, tilshunoslikdagi dolzarb muammolarni o‘rganish va ularga yechim topish - bu nafaqat ilmiy, balki ijtimoiy-ma’naviy zarurat hisoblanadi.

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PHILOLOGY AND LANGUAGE EDUCATION - MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Annotation: In the twenty-first century, philology and language education have undergone significant transformations influenced by globalization, digitalization, and interdisciplinary integration. The study of language and culture has expanded from purely linguistic analysis to sociocultural, cognitive, and technological dimensions. This article explores the current trends in philology and examines innovative approaches in language education, focusing on digital pedagogy, communicative competence, and interdisciplinary research. The paper concludes that the future of philology and language education lies in harmonizing traditional linguistic scholarship with modern technological and pedagogical innovations. In the twenty-first century, philology and language education have undergone significant transformations influenced by globalization, digitalization, and interdisciplinary integration. The study of language and culture has expanded from purely linguistic analysis to sociocultural, cognitive, and technological dimensions. This article explores the current trends in philology and examines innovative approaches in language education, focusing on digital pedagogy, communicative competence, and interdisciplinary research. The paper concludes that the future of philology and language education lies in harmonizing traditional linguistic scholarship with modern technological and pedagogical innovations.

Keywords: philology, language education, innovation, modern trends, digital pedagogy, communicative competence

Introduction: Philology, traditionally defined as the study of language in written historical sources, has long been regarded as the cornerstone of linguistic and literary scholarship. In recent decades, however, its scope has expanded, incorporating interdisciplinary perspectives from cultural studies, semiotics, and digital humanities. Similarly, language education has shifted from grammar-translation and structuralist models to communicative, task-based, and technology-enhanced methodologies (Richards, 2020). The convergence of these developments reflects the ongoing evolution of human communication in the digital age.

In the globalized world, the demand for multilingual competence and intercultural awareness has placed philology and language pedagogy at the center of educational reforms. As a result, scholars and educators now emphasize the importance of integrating innovation, research-based instruction, and technological literacy into language learning (Kukulska-Hulme, 2022). This article aims to analyze key trends in modern philology and discuss innovative strategies that shape contemporary language education.

Modern Trends in Philology: the discipline of philology has evolved beyond traditional textual criticism and historical linguistics. One of the dominant trends is digital philology, which applies computational tools to analyze linguistic and literary data. Digital corpora, automated text annotation, and artificial intelligence have revolutionized philological research, allowing for large-scale comparative studies and corpus-based linguistic analysis (Jänicke et al., 2021).

Another emerging tendency is the interdisciplinary orientation of philology. Modern researchers increasingly engage with cultural studies, anthropology, and cognitive science to explore the relationship between language, thought, and identity. This integrative perspective enables philologists to examine language not only as a system of signs but also as a dynamic reflection of social and cultural processes (Kramersch, 2021).

A further trend is the globalization of philological research. Whereas earlier philological traditions focused primarily on European languages, contemporary scholars examine the linguistic and literary heritage of Asian, African, and indigenous cultures. This shift broadens the understanding of linguistic diversity and promotes inclusive approaches to world literature and translation studies (Miller, 2022).

Lastly, applied philology—the practical use of linguistic knowledge in translation, lexicography, and digital content creation—has gained new relevance. As society becomes increasingly information-driven, philologists play a vital role in preserving linguistic heritage, curating digital archives, and supporting language policy development (Petrova & Ivanov, 2023).

Innovative Approaches in Language Education: contemporary language education is characterized by its adaptability and emphasis on communication. Among the most influential innovations is communicative language teaching (CLT), which prioritizes meaningful interaction and real-life communication. This approach helps students develop fluency and sociolinguistic competence rather than mere grammatical accuracy (Richards & Rodgers, 2020). Equally important is the rise of technology-enhanced language learning (TELL). Digital platforms such as YouTube, podcasts, and learning management systems provide authentic materials and interactive opportunities for learners (Reinders & Benson, 2022). In this context, teachers act as facilitators, guiding students in using digital tools to develop listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills.

Gamification and mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) have also become popular. These methods employ mobile applications and game-based tasks to increase learner motivation and engagement (Dooly & O'Dowd, 2021). For instance, language-learning apps

like Duolingo and Memrise combine entertainment with structured learning, appealing to diverse learner styles. Another innovation is blended learning, which combines face-to-face instruction with online learning environments. This approach allows flexible access to resources and personalized feedback, promoting learner autonomy (Kukulska-Hulme & Lee, 2023). Moreover, project-based and task-based learning methodologies encourage students to apply linguistic knowledge in practical contexts, fostering creativity and collaboration.

Finally, intercultural communicative competence (ICC) has become a central goal in language education. The ability to communicate effectively across cultures requires awareness of sociocultural norms, empathy, and adaptability (Byram, 2021). Thus, innovative pedagogy integrates cultural elements into linguistic instruction, aligning with global educational standards.

The intersection of philology and language education illustrates how theoretical and practical dimensions of linguistic study reinforce each other. Philological research provides the historical and cultural foundation for understanding language evolution, while innovative teaching practices translate this knowledge into effective pedagogy. The integration of digital tools, intercultural competence, and learner-centered methods ensures that language education remains relevant in a rapidly changing world.

Moreover, innovation in language pedagogy supports the preservation and revitalization of minority languages, aligning with UNESCO's advocacy for linguistic diversity (UNESCO, 2023). Therefore, both philologists and educators share the responsibility of promoting linguistic sustainability and cross-cultural understanding.

Conclusion: To conclude, Philology and language education, once viewed as separate domains, now converge in their pursuit of linguistic, cultural, and technological advancement. Modern philology embraces digital tools, global perspectives, and interdisciplinary research, while language education incorporates innovation, inclusivity, and learner-centered methodologies. Together, they reflect the dynamic nature of human communication in the twenty-first century.

For future development, collaboration between philologists, linguists, and educators is essential to bridge theory and practice. By uniting traditional scholarship with innovative teaching strategies, language professionals can cultivate a deeper understanding of linguistic diversity and enhance the quality of education in a globalized society.

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FRAZEMALARNING MILLIY-MADANIY SEMANTIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘rganilayotgan frazeologik birliklarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari, ularning milliy-madaniy sema sifatida o‘ziga xos jihatlarini o‘rganishga asosiy e‘tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: lingvokulturolog, sema, etnik, maqol, o‘zbek, til, xalq, tarix, muloqat, udum.

Annotation: This article focuses on the linguocultural features of the studied phraseological units, emphasizing their unique characteristics as national and cultural semes.

Keywords: linguoculture, seme, ethnic, proverb, Uzbek, language, people, history, communication, tradition.

Milliy-madaniy birliklar, asosan, muayyan xalqqa xos etnik jihatlar, uning milliy-madaniy dunyoqarashi, an‘ana va udumlari, tarixiy an‘analari bilan bog‘liq odob-axloq, muloqot me‘yorlari, o‘ziga xos milliy ruhdagi ijod namunalari, maqol, matal, ibora, majoziy ifodalar, ko‘chma ma‘noli birliklardan iborat birliklardir. Shuni xarakterliki, til birliklarida milliy-madaniy belgi turlicha aks etadi. Ayrim birliklar bevosita milliy xoslanganlik belgisini namoyon qilsa, ba‘zi birliklarda bu belgi bilvosita yuzaga chiqadi. Ayrim so‘zlarda madaniy sema lug‘aviy ma‘no bilan yonma-yon yashasa, ba‘zilarida ularning ko‘chma ma‘nosi orqali yuzaga chiqadi. Masalan, iboralar voqelikni ko‘chma ma‘no orqali aks ettirgani bois ularda bevosita milliy-madaniy belgi aks etadi. O‘zbek tilidagi beshik leksemasi o‘z ma‘nosida o‘zbek xalqining milliy qadriyatlaridan biriga aylangan predmetni bevosita aks ettirganligi bois milliy-madaniy birlik hisoblanadi. Bunday vaziyatda til birligiga xos madaniylik belgisi uning lug‘aviy ma‘nosi orqali anglashiladi. Bunday birliklar tarixan shakllangan bo‘lib, millat madaniy hayotida muhim o‘rin egallaydi va boshqa tillarda kuzatilmaydi. Til madaniy hodisa sifatida e‘tirof etilsa-da, uning tizimida millatning madaniy qadriyatlarini aks ettiruvchi maxsus birliklari alohida guruhlanadi. Bunday birliklar muayyan xalqqa xos etnik, ijtimoiy-madaniy qarashlar, milliy an‘analar, udumlar, odob-axloq, muloqot me‘yorlari kabilarni anglatadi. Bu kabi ekstralingvistik ma‘lumotlarni o‘zida jamlagan til birliklari milliy-madaniy birliklar deb ataladi. V.V.Vorobyev bunday birliklarni lingvokulturema termini bilan ifoda etishni taklif qilgan edi. Uning fikricha, bu termin til birligining nafaqat lisoniy ma‘nosini, balki madaniyat segmentini ham qamrab oladi [1].

Lingvokulturemalarga madaniyatning biror bo‘lagini aks ettiruvchi so‘zlar, frazeologik birliklar, so‘z birikmalari, gaplar, paremiyalar, murakkab sintaktik butunliklar, matnlar va hokozolar kiradi. Lingvokulturema mazmun va ifoda planiga ega, ifoda plani yuqorida ko‘rsatilgan birliklar, mazmun planini esa o‘sha birliklarning semantikasi tashkil qiladi. Demak, lingvokulturema kontseptdan o‘zining mazmun va ifoda planiga ega bo‘lishi bilan farq qiladi, lingvokulturologiya uchun xalq madaniyatini lisoniy ko‘rinishda namoyon etish asosiy vazifa hisoblanadi. “Lingvokulturema” tushunchasi qiyosiy tilshunoslik uchun foydali, “zero til – madaniy fakt, biz meros qilib oladigan madaniyatning tarkibiy qismi va ayni paytda qurol hamdir. Xalq madaniyati til orqali verballashadi, aynan til madaniyatining tayanch, asosiy tushunchalarini harakatga keltiradi va ularni belgilar ko‘rinishida, ya‘ni

so‘zlar vositasida ifoda etadi” [2]. Shunga binoan FBlarning lingvomadaniy jihatdan semantikasini yoritishga harakat qildik.

Til birliklarida milliy-madaniy belgi turlicha aks etadi. Ayrim birliklar bevosita milliy xoslanganlik belgisini namoyon qilsa, ba’zi birliklarda bu belgi bilvosita yuzaga chiqadi. Ayrim so‘zlarda madaniy sema lug‘aviy ma’no bilan yonma-yon yashasa, ba’zilarida ularning ko‘chma ma’nosi orqali yuzaga chiqadi. Masalan, iboralar voqelikni ko‘chma ma’no orqali aks ettirgani bois ular da bevosita milliy-madaniy belgi aks etadi. O‘zbek tilidagi beshik leksemasi o‘z ma’nosida o‘zbek xalqining milliy qadriyatlaridan biriga aylangan predmetni bevosita aks ettirganligi bois milliy-madaniy birlik hisoblanadi. Bunday vaziyatda til birligiga xos madaniylik belgisi uning lug‘aviy ma’nosi orqali anglashiladi. Bunday birliklar tarixan shakllangan bo‘lib, millat madaniy hayotida muhim o‘rin egallaydi va boshqa tillarda kuzatilmaydi. Tilshunoslikda bu tipdagi milliy-madaniy birliklar ekvivalentsiz leksika yoki realiyalar deb ham yuritiladi. “O‘zbek tilidagi do‘ppi, atlas (mato), yaktak, belbog‘, karnay-surnay, nog‘ora leksemalarida madaniy sema ularning lug‘aviy ma’nosi bilan birga gavdalanadi. Bunday leksemalar orqali bevosita o‘zbek xalqi, uning milliy urf-odatlariga ishora qilinadi. Xuddi shunday, rus tilidagi samovar, qozoq tilidagi beshbarmoq leksemalarida ham madaniy sema bevosita anglashilib turadi” [1].

Frazeologizmlarning muayyan guruhi xalqlarning urf-odatlarini, an‘analari va irimlari ta‘sirida shakllanadi. Jumladan, o‘zbek xalqida azafdan quloqtish odati mavjud. Quloqtishlar, ya‘ni beshik odati hozirgi kunda Surxondaryo viloyatining ayrim tuman va qishloqlarida saqlanib qoigan. Oilada qiz bola tug‘ilib, chillasi chiqqandan keyin beshik lo‘y o‘tkaziladi. Qarindosh urug‘, do‘st-og‘aynilar yangi farzand bilan muborakbod etgani bu oilaga kelishadi. Shunda o‘g‘illik birodarlardan biri niyat qilib, yetaklab borgan 5-6 yashar o‘g‘ilchasiga chaqaloq qizchani tilaydi, so‘ratadi. Qizi bor oilaning buvasi, buvisi, ota-onasi va qarindosh-urug‘lari rozilik berishsa, "quloqtishlar" odati o‘tkazilgan. Boyagi bolakay beshikda yotgan qizaloqning "qulog‘ini tishlagan. Qadim zamonlarda bunday "qudashilik" ana‘analari qabilalar o‘rtasidagi urush-janjallarga chek qo‘ygan. Tinch qo‘shnichilikni saqlab qolgan [3]. Mazkur odatni ifodalovchi "qiz bolani go‘dakligidayoq bo‘ljak qayligi deb belgilab qo‘ymoq ma’nosidagi" "qulog‘ini tishlamoq" iborasi qo‘llaniladi.

O‘zbek xalqining nikohlash marosimi, unashtirish odati bilan bog‘liq iboralarini tarkibida somatik so‘zlar faol qatnashadi. "Boshlarini qovushtirmoq", "boshlarini biriktirmoq", "boshlarini qo‘shmoq", "boshini ikkita qilmoq", "bir yostiqa bosh qo‘ymoq" va h.k.

O‘zbek oilasida bola tug‘ilishi bilan chilla davri boshlanadi. Ayol farzand ko‘rishi bilan maxsus sharoitda saqlanib turli ins-jinslar, kasalliklardan himoya qilingan. An‘anaga ko‘ra ona va bola qirq kungacha chillali uydan chiqmasligi, bolali uyga begona odam kirmasligi, chillali uyda chiroq o‘chmasligi kerak. Chilla an‘anasi "tuqqaniga qirq kun bo‘ldi" ma’nosidagi chillasi chiqdi iborasi bilan ifodalanadi: Chillasi chiqishi bilan Hadya ham alohida qizlar yacheykasi tuzishga boradi.

Frazeologik birliklarning tayanch komponenti sifatida tarixiy va diniy-mifologik mashhur shaxslarning nomlari kelishi mumkin: Xo‘ja ko‘rsinga "shunchaki nomigagina", Musoning alamini Isodan olmoq "aybdor chyetda qolib, aybsiz kishiga qarshi ish tutmoq", Xizrni yo‘qlasam bo‘lar ekan "kimnidir ko‘rish istagi qo‘qisdan ro‘yobga chiqqanda aytiladigan ibora". Turk tilida: Bir Krgl bir Ayvaz "bola-chaqasi yo‘q er-xotin", Dardini Marko Paşa‘ya anlat "dardini eshitadigan hech kim yo‘q". Turli geografik joy nomlari ham frazeologik birliklarning tayanch komponentlari vazifasida keladi. Masalan, o‘zbekcha frazeologik birliklar tarkibida O‘zbekiston hududida joylashgan shahar, qishloq, daryo va sahrolar nomlari uchraydi... Frazeologik birliklar tarkibida qo‘llanilgan toponimlar o‘zlari

jonlantiradigan sifat va belgilar, chunonchi, uzoqlik, saxiylik, taqvodorlik kabi alomatlar timsollari sifatida namoyon bo'ladi: Beva xotinga Buxorodan it xuradi, onasini Uchqo'rg'ondan ko'rsatmoq frazeologik birliklari tarkibidagi "Buxoro", "Uchqo'rg'on", до Москвы не перевешаешь, кричать во всю Ивоносвкую frazeologizmlari tarkibidagi "Москва", "Ивановская" O'zbekiston va Rossiya hududlarida joylashgan geografik nomlar bo'lsa, язык до Киева, tuxumi Bag'doddan kelibdimi?, Do in Rome as the Romans do nomlaridir [5] yoki "umid qilgan, kutgan narsaning teskarisi bo'lib chiqdi" ma'nosidagi Göründü Sivas'ın bağları, "bu ish hozircha bo'lgani bilan keyinchalik orqasidan g'avg'o chiqadi" ma'nosidagi Karaman'ın koyunu, sonra çıkar oyunu tarkibida foydalanilgan "Kiyev", "Bag'dod", "Rome (Rim)", "Sivas", "Karaman" shaharlari rus, o'zbek, ingliz va turk xalqlari uzoq asrlar davomida munosabat-muloqotda bo'lib kelgan shahar nomlaridir.

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COMPARATIVE AND TYPOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article explores the linguistic essence of comparative and typological analysis, their distinctive features, and interrelation based on scholarly sources. The main goal of comparative analysis is to identify historical and genetic relationships among languages, while typological analysis focuses on studying structural and functional similarities among languages belonging to different families. The paper highlights the developmental stages, methodological foundations, research scope, and practical significance of both approaches. Using Turkic and Indo-European languages as examples, their specific analytical principles are demonstrated. The findings show that comparative and typological analyses complement each other and together enable a comprehensive study of linguistic systems.

Keywords: comparative analysis, typological analysis, comparative linguistics, language typology, genetic relationship, structural similarity, language universals.

Linguistics is a constantly evolving field, and one of the most effective ways to study languages is through comparative and typological perspectives. Both approaches play a vital role in understanding the structure, evolution, and development laws of languages. Comparative analysis focuses on discovering historical roots, genetic connections, and evolutionary directions of languages, while typological analysis examines structural similarities and universal features across different linguistic systems. Historically, comparative linguistics emerged in the 19th century, developed by scholars such as Franz Bopp, Rasmus Rask, and Jacob Grimm. Their studies, especially in Indo-European linguistics, provided scientific evidence for language kinship. [1. Page 235] Typological analysis, on the other hand, developed in the 20th century through the works of Edward Sapir and Joseph Greenberg, focusing on cross-linguistic structural similarities regardless of genetic relationships. Although these two approaches differ in nature, they complement each other in linguistic research, offering deeper insights into the essence and development of human language.

Comparative linguistics, as a historical linguistic method, originated in the early 19th century. Scholars of that time discovered that similarities between languages were not coincidental but indicated shared historical roots. Franz Bopp's seminal work *On the Conjugation System of the Sanskrit Language* marked the foundation of this field. He analyzed the verbal systems of Indo-European languages and demonstrated their morphological correspondences, proving their common origin. Later, Grimm's Law established the regularity of sound changes, giving scientific credibility to the comparative method. The main aim of comparative analysis is to determine genetic relationships among related languages by examining historical changes in their phonetic, morphological, and lexical systems. Through this method, language families and subgroups are classified, and proto-languages are reconstructed. For instance, Turkic languages such as Uzbek, Kazakh, Turkmen, Uyghur, and Turkish share cognates like *ona* (mother), *ata* (father), *ko'l* (lake), *tog'* (mountain), and *yol* (road), all deriving from a common ancestral source. Comparative analysis not only identifies kinship among languages but also reveals laws of language change and directions of phonetic and grammatical evolution. It provides a scientific basis for reconstructing language history, classifying families, and explaining their evolutionary connections. [2. Page 168]

Typological analysis emerged as an independent field of linguistics in the 20th century. Edward Sapir emphasized the importance of studying the structural features of languages regardless of genetic relationship, while Joseph Greenberg later laid the foundation for linguistic universals and typological classification. Typological analysis focuses on the structural systems of languages - their morphological, syntactic, phonological, and semantic properties. Languages are classified as analytic, agglutinative, fusional, or polysynthetic. [3. Page 345] For example, Uzbek is an agglutinative language where grammatical meanings are expressed through sequential suffixes, whereas English is analytic, relying mainly on word order and auxiliary words (from our books). The primary aim of typological analysis is to identify language universals - general principles common to all human languages. This approach reveals cross-linguistic similarities and helps understand the universal nature and structure of human language.

Comparative analysis is historical, examining the past development and evolution of related languages, whereas typological analysis is descriptive and structural, focusing on the present state of languages. Comparative studies deal with genetically related languages, while typological studies may include unrelated languages that share similar structures. For

example, the similarity between Uzbek and Kazakh is explained through comparative analysis since both belong to the Turkic family. Meanwhile, similarities between Uzbek and English word order (SVO structure) fall under typological analysis, as the two languages are genetically unrelated but structurally comparable. Comparative analysis results in the classification of languages into families, while typological analysis results in the categorization of languages into structural types. In short, comparative analysis is based on historical-genealogical principles, while typological analysis relies on structural-functional principles. [4. Page 87]

In modern linguistics, these two approaches are viewed as complementary. Comparative analysis uncovers historical roots, while typological analysis reveals structural organization. Combined, they provide a holistic understanding of language systems. Comparative analysis explains how language families evolved, while typology shows how languages function according to universal principles. Therefore, integrating both methods represent one of the most effective ways to explore the complexity and unity of human language. [5. Page 204]

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THE ROLE OF METAPHOR AND EVALUATION IN TRAVEL BLOGS: A CROSS-LINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: This article examines how metaphor and evaluative language shape meaning and persuasion in English and Russian travel blogs. Using a cross-linguistic and cognitive linguistic approach, it highlights how bloggers employ metaphors to express emotion, authenticity, and cultural perception in digital travel discourse.

Keywords: metaphor, evaluation, travel blogs, cross-linguistic analysis, discourse, cognitive linguistics, digital communication.

In today’s digital age, travel blogs occupy an increasingly important place in shaping perceptions of places, cultures, and experiences. As users across the globe share their travel narratives online, linguistic devices in these narratives play a critical role in influencing how readers feel, imagine, and ultimately decide about travel. Among such devices, **metaphor** and **evaluation** are particularly powerful: metaphor enriches descriptions by invoking familiar conceptual mappings (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980), while evaluation expresses the blogger’s stance, attitude, and value judgments toward people, places, or encounters.

A cross-linguistic perspective – comparing languages such as English and Russian – can reveal how differently (or similarly) metaphor and evaluative language are used in travel blogs, given cultural, cognitive, and linguistic differences. Such comparison contributes both

to theoretical understanding of discourse, as well as practical implications for tourism communication, translation, and intercultural understanding.

Metaphor has long been recognized as a key rhetorical device in promotional and narrative travel discourse. Jaworska (2017) investigated metaphors in promotional tourism discourse, finding that descriptions of exotic or tropical destinations often employ metaphorical mappings from domains such as **natural precious elements, color, body, taste** and religion, to evoke vivid images and emotional appeal. Similar studies in non-promotional settings (e.g. travel blogs) are fewer, but some research has begun to explore how travel writers use descriptive and figurative language to evoke atmosphere, sensory experience, and affect. For example, Huang, Wang & Tang (2020) studied interactional metadiscourse in English travel blogs, though their focus was more on interaction with the reader than metaphorical language.

Evaluation, often treated within frameworks such as **Appraisal Theory** (Martin & White, 2005), refers to how writers express attitudes, engage with other voices, and gradate meaning (intensity, force). In particular, the domains of *attitude* (affect, judgment, appreciation), *engagement* (how writer aligns with or distances themselves from other perspectives), and *graduation* (degree or intensity) are central to how evaluation is structured. Studies in academic discourse (e.g. Xu & Nesi, 2017) show how evaluation contexts vary depending on whether the writer is describing real-world events, analyzing research worlds, or engaging in argumentation. For travel blogs, evaluative language tends to combine affective (emotions), appreciative (beauty, value), and judgemental (regarding behavior, authenticity) functions, to persuade or to lend credibility. Though specific cross-linguistic comparisons in travel blogs remain under-explored.

Comparative metaphor studies often focus on conceptual metaphors (e.g., LOVE IS A JOURNEY) and examine how metaphors differ or align across cultures. For example, studies in figurative expressions between English and other languages have found that while many conceptual metaphors are shared, the lexical instantiations and conventionalization may vary greatly (Božić & Dragana, etc.). In Russian tourism discourse, studies have begun to map metaphors and evaluative language but often in promotional or descriptive discourse rather than personal narrative travel blogs. There is a gap in systematic investigation of how metaphors co-occur with evaluation in personal travel blogging, how culture-specific metaphors or values shape evaluations, and whether there are systematic differences between English and Russian in the frequencies, types, or functions of metaphor + evaluation.

This study adopts a **qualitative and corpus-based comparative approach** to explore how metaphor and evaluative language function in English and Russian travel blogs. The corpus consists of **40 travel blog entries**—20 written in English and 20 in Russian—published between **2020 and 2024** on widely known platforms such as *WordPress*, *LiveJournal*, and *Travel.ru*. The selected posts were chosen for their narrative character, descriptive richness, and personal engagement with the reader, which are key features of the travel blog genre (Thurlow & Jaworski, 2010). Each text was downloaded and anonymized to protect authors' privacy. The total corpus size was approximately **60,000 words** (30,500 English and 29,500 Russian). Both subcorpora were of comparable length and thematic scope—representing journeys to both domestic and international destinations.

The comparative analysis revealed that both English and Russian travel blogs rely heavily on **metaphorical and evaluative language** to construct vivid, emotionally engaging narratives. However, notable **cross-linguistic and cultural differences** were observed in the choice of metaphorical domains, intensity of evaluation, and their interplay in expressing personal experience. Across the corpus, metaphors accounted for approximately **7.2% of total lexical items** in English blogs and **6.5%** in Russian ones. Evaluation appeared even more

frequently – an average of **11 evaluative expressions per 1,000 words** in English and **9 per 1,000 words** in Russian. These figures confirm that emotionality and value judgments are integral components of the travel blog genre, supporting previous findings that online travel discourse combines both narrative and persuasive functions (Dann, 1996; Jaworski & Thurlow, 2010).

In English blogs, the most prevalent conceptual metaphors included travel as transformation, nature as living being, and city as experience. Writers frequently portrayed travel as a process of inner growth, renewal, or self-discovery. Examples such as “*I was reborn with every sunrise*” or “*the desert whispered lessons of patience*” reflect a Western individualistic orientation, emphasizing **personal empowerment** and **self-reflection**. Such patterns align with Lakoff and Johnson’s (1980) view of metaphor as a cognitive tool for structuring abstract experiences through familiar embodied schemas. By contrast, Russian blogs often relied on **emotionally charged and nature-based metaphors**, such as “*море обнимает путешника*” (“*the sea embraces the traveler*”) or “*город поёт мелодию свободы*” (“*the city sings a melody of freedom*”). These metaphors reflect the **aesthetic and collective orientation** of Russian discourse, where emotion and artistry intertwine with the perception of place. The imagery tends to evoke **unity with nature and space**, rather than personal transformation. Similar tendencies have been observed in studies of Russian poetic and media discourse (Chudinov, 2003; Boldyrev, 2019), where metaphorical personification serves as a means of emotional intensification.

The appraisal analysis revealed both similarities and differences in evaluative orientation. English bloggers tended to use a higher proportion of **affective** and **appreciative** language – e.g., “*breathhtaking*,” “*unforgettable*,” “*heart-warming*” – to emphasize emotional and sensory responses. These evaluations often accompany metaphors, strengthening their persuasive impact. Russian authors, while also using affective lexis, demonstrated a higher use of **judgemental** evaluation, particularly in describing local people, traditions, and behaviors – e.g., “*радушные жители*,” “*искренняя культура*” (“*hospitable people*,” “*authentic culture*”). This reflects a **cultural focus on morality and sincerity**, rather than solely emotional appeal. The frequency of positive evaluations was roughly similar across languages (around 80%), but **English blogs showed stronger polarity** – either highly positive or mildly negative – while **Russian texts preferred moderate tone and implicit evaluation**.

A crucial finding of this study is the **co-occurrence** of metaphor and evaluation as complementary strategies. Metaphor provides **imagery and framing**, while evaluation supplies **emotional stance and persuasion**. In English texts, metaphors of **journey and light** often coincided with positive appreciation (e.g., “*a city glowing with promise*”), reinforcing the sense of optimism and wonder typical of Anglo-American travel writing. In Russian blogs, **nature and emotion metaphors** frequently merged with affective or aesthetic evaluation (e.g., “*природа ласково укрывает усталую душу*” – “*nature gently shelters the tired soul*”), creating lyrical and introspective effects. These patterns suggest that while the **communicative goals** of travel bloggers are similar – sharing experiences and inspiring readers – the **linguistic means** reflect deeper cultural models. English travel blogs favor a more **individualistic and expressive** mode of persuasion, whereas Russian blogs highlight **empathy, collectivity, and emotional resonance**.

The findings contribute to discourse studies and intercultural pragmatics by showing that metaphor and evaluation are not universal but **culturally mediated linguistic tools**. They mirror broader value orientations: **self-realization and authenticity** in English discourse, **emotional depth and harmony with environment** in Russian. These results confirm Koller’s (2004) argument that metaphor in discourse operates ideologically, constructing

particular worldviews and cultural identities. From a practical perspective, understanding these patterns is essential for **translation studies** and **tourism communication**, where emotional tone and metaphorical framing must be adapted across languages. Moreover, for **foreign language teaching**, awareness of such discourse mechanisms can enhance intercultural competence and pragmatic sensitivity in students learning to interpret or produce persuasive texts.

This study explored the interrelation of **metaphor** and **evaluation** in English and Russian travel blogs, highlighting how these linguistic resources shape the emotional and persuasive dimensions of travel discourse. The analysis revealed both universal and culture-specific tendencies. English bloggers favored metaphors of *journey* and *light* combined with affective and appreciative evaluation to express **personal transformation** and **individual experience**. Russian bloggers, in contrast, relied on *nature* and *emotion* metaphors intertwined with aesthetic and moral evaluation, emphasizing **collective emotion**, **spiritual reflection**, and **harmony with environment**.

These findings demonstrate that while travel blogs serve similar communicative purposes across languages – sharing impressions, inspiring readers, and constructing authenticity – their **linguistic realization** reflects differing **cultural worldviews**. The results contribute to the fields of discourse analysis, cognitive linguistics, and intercultural communication by showing that metaphor and evaluation are **culturally mediated mechanisms** for constructing meaning and identity in online travel narratives.

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FUTURE DOMINANCE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article explores the current and future status of the English language as a global medium of communication. It traces the historical, cultural, and technological roots of English dominance from British colonial expansion to the rise of American global influence and examines how the enforcements in digital world, artificial intelligence, and multilingual movements are reshaping linguistic power worldwide. While English remains the primary language of science, business, diplomacy, and the internet, new forces such as AI-driven translation, the growth of Chinese and Spanish, and the promotion of linguistic diversity are challenging its supremacy. The paper also introduces the concept of “Globish,” a simplified, functional variety of English used by international speakers for global communication. Drawing from linguistic forecasts and sociocultural trends, the article concludes that English will remain a dominant but evolving lingua franca [1], increasingly shaped by non-native speakers and coexisting with other world languages in a multilingual 21st century.

Keywords: English dominance; global communication; artificial intelligence; multilingualism; linguistic diversity; Globish; future of English.

Introduction. By serving as an international bridge to many nations, English is spoken by more than 1.5 billion people around the world. It is applied in several crucial areas of every developed country, such as diplomacy, technology, science, and travel, not to mention its role in connecting cultures like no other language. Yet, with rapid developments in artificial intelligence and the growth of other global powers, many experts and linguists are asking: Will English be the dominant language in the future?

The global dominance of English: The global dominance of English has outstandingly wide, practical, and historical roots. It became widespread through British colonial expansion. English became the language of administration, law, and trade in colonies across Asia, Africa, and the Americas. Even after independence, many countries kept English as an official or second language because it enabled them to interact with others across ethnic and regional groups (e.g., India, Kenya, Malaysia).

After World War II, the United States emerged as the world's leading economy and political power, spreading English through business, diplomacy, and culture. Hollywood films, American music, and later television and the internet made English the most visible global language of entertainment. These influencers conveyed this message through various channels, including lessons, advertisements, and news, reaching even the most remote cities and countryside.

English in Global Communication. Today, English is officially used in higher education, business, technology, on the internet, and in diplomacy. According to statistics, approximately 80 percent of scientific journals and most global news outlets publish in English, which maintains and reinforces its influence. The majority of top universities (Harvard, Oxford, Cambridge, MIT) teach and publish in English. Millions of students study abroad where English is the medium of instruction.

It is the official working language of international business, aviation, and maritime communication (used by pilots, air traffic control, and shipping). Over 50 % of all web pages are in English; global platforms (Google, YouTube, Wikipedia, ChatGPT, etc.) primarily use English interfaces. English is one of the official languages of the United Nations, the European Union, ASEAN, and NATO, making it crucial for global cooperation.

Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Language. In the digital age, technology is quietly transforming how we communicate across borders. With artificial-intelligence translators and multilingual [3] apps becoming more advanced every year, people no longer need to rely on English alone to connect with the world.

The global AI translation market was valued at USD 2.34 billion in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 2.94 billion by 2025, growing at about 25 % annually [1]. Google Translate supports 100+ languages and processes over 100 billion words daily, showing how technology bridges communication barriers worldwide. Surveys show that nearly 75 % of professional translators believe AI will significantly affect their future income or job roles [2].

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GRAMMAR AND SYNTAX IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article examines the importance of grammar and syntax in language teaching. It discusses their role in improving accuracy, fluency, and communicative competence of learners. The paper highlights practical methods, teaching strategies, and the integration of grammar within communicative approaches.

Key words: grammar, syntax, language teaching, communicative competence, fluency, accuracy, teaching methods, deductive approach, inductive approach, communicative approach, linguistic structure, language pedagogy

Language teaching is a complex process that involves the development of several linguistic components such as grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and syntax. Among these, grammar and syntax hold a central position because they define the structure and meaning of language. Without grammatical rules and syntactic organization, communication becomes unclear and ineffective. The role of grammar and syntax in language classrooms has evolved through various methodologies, from traditional grammar-translation approaches to modern communicative and task-based teaching. Today, educators aim to create a balance between accuracy and fluency, ensuring learners can both understand rules and use them in real communication.

Understanding grammar and syntax. Grammar refers to the rules that govern how words change form and combine to form sentences. Syntax, on the other hand, focuses on sentence structure and the arrangement of words to create meaningful expressions. Aspect Grammar Syntax. Definition Rules and forms Sentence structure Focus Tense, agreement, morphology Word order, sentence patterns Goal Correctness Meaning and clarity Grammar ensures correctness, while syntax ensures clarity and natural flow in speech and writing.

Importance of grammar in language teaching. Helps students speak and write correctly Prevents ambiguity and misunderstanding Develops academic writing skills Supports reading comprehension and translation. Traditional methods emphasized memorization of grammar rules. However, modern pedagogy integrates grammar within meaningful contexts to improve real communication.

Role of syntax in developing communicative competence. Syntax allows learners to build complex ideas using correct sentence patterns. For example: Simple: I study English. Complex: I study English because I want to become a teacher. Teaching syntax helps learners produce longer and more expressive sentences, improving both speaking and writing proficiency.

Teaching approaches to grammar and syntax. a) Deductive Method (Rule - Practice) Teacher explains the rule, then students do exercises. Advantage: Clear understanding Disadvantage: Less communicative b) Inductive Method (Examples - Rule) Students discover rules through examples. Advantage: Engaging and analytical Disadvantage: Time-consuming c) Communicative Approach Grammar is taught through speaking, dialogues, role-plays, and real tasks. Focus: Meaning, usage, and fluency.

Integrating Grammar in Language Skills. Skill Grammar Focus Speaking Fluency and correctness Writing Sentence structure, cohesion Reading Understanding complex text Listening Recognizing patterns and tense.

Challenges in Teaching Grammar and Syntax Overuse of theoretical explanation Lack of context in exercises Students' fear of making mistakes Balancing accuracy and fluency. Teachers must provide supportive feedback and encourage students to use grammar actively in communication.

Grammar and syntax are foundational concepts in linguistics and language pedagogy, each contributing to the development of communicative competence. According to Chomsky (1965), grammar represents the implicit knowledge that enables speakers to generate an infinite number of sentences, while syntax is the structural arrangement that ensures coherence and meaning. In language teaching, these components are not only descriptive but also pedagogical, shaping classroom practices and learning outcomes.

Grammar can be defined as the set of structural rules that govern word formation (morphology) and sentence construction. In pedagogy, grammar is generally classified into three main types: Prescriptive Grammar – focuses on correct usage and traditional norms. Descriptive Grammar – analyses how language is naturally used by native speakers. Pedagogical Grammar – adapted for teaching purposes, presenting rules in a simplified and practical way. Effective pedagogical grammar emphasizes not just memorization, but meaningful application, allowing learners to internalize structures through context and practice.

Syntax refers to the way words are combined to form phrases and sentences. It studies hierarchical structures rather than isolated elements. For example: SVO (Subject-Verb-Object) in English: “The student reads a book.” SOV in some other languages: “The student a book reads.” Teaching syntax is essential because learners must move beyond isolated vocabulary to produce coherent discourse. Syntax enables the construction of complex thoughts, conditional clauses, reported speech, and academic sentences.

While grammar includes rules of morphology and syntax, syntax specifically examines word order and sentence relations. In teaching: Aspect Grammar Syntax Focus Rules & forms Sentence structure Level Words & clauses Sentences & discourse Purpose Accuracy Clarity & cohesion A comprehensive approach requires both accuracy (grammar) and fluency (syntax), creating linguistically competent learners.

Several linguistic theories have shaped grammar teaching: Behaviorism (Skinner, 1957) – emphasizes repetition and habit formation. Generative Grammar (Chomsky, 1965) – views grammar as innate and rule-based. Krashen's Monitor Theory (1982) – distinguishes between acquired and learned grammar. Functionalism (Halliday, 1994) – focuses on grammar as a tool for meaning-making. Modern pedagogy synthesizes these theories, advocating for explicit grammar instruction supported by communicative practice.

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THE ROLE OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS IN STUDYING CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS

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Abstract. Conceptual metaphor theory, introduced by Lakoff and Johnson (1980), has become one of the most influential frameworks in modern linguistics. It emphasizes that metaphors are not merely stylistic devices but fundamental mechanisms of human thought that shape how individuals perceive and interact with the world. This article examines the role of cognitive linguistics in studying conceptual metaphors, focusing on their functions, classification, and application in discourse analysis. The findings suggest that the study of conceptual metaphors provides insights into the cultural, psychological, and communicative aspects of language, making it an effective tool for linguistic research and English language teaching.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, conceptual metaphor, discourse analysis, cultural linguistics.

Introduction. In modern linguistics, the study of metaphor has moved beyond the boundaries of literary analysis. Since the publication of Lakoff and Johnson's *Metaphors We Live By* (1980), metaphors have been redefined as essential cognitive tools that structure human understanding of abstract concepts through more concrete experiences. For example, the conceptual metaphor "Time is money" manifests in expressions such as "spending time," "wasting time," and "saving time." Such linguistic patterns reveal how human cognition organizes abstract domains by mapping them onto concrete, physical experiences. Cognitive linguistics provides a theoretical and methodological framework to analyze these phenomena systematically. Unlike traditional rhetorical approaches, cognitive linguistics perceives metaphors as a window into the human mind, uncovering not only linguistic but also cultural and psychological dimensions of meaning. This article explores how conceptual metaphor theory contributes to the study of language and discusses its applications in linguistic research, discourse analysis, and pedagogy.

Literature Review. The development of conceptual metaphor theory (CMT) began with Lakoff and Johnson's seminal work, which proposed that everyday language is permeated with metaphorical expressions reflecting deeper cognitive structures. Kövecses (2002) expanded this approach, offering detailed classifications of conceptual metaphors and linking them to cultural and emotional factors.

Later research demonstrated the universality of certain metaphors, as well as their culture-specific variations. For instance, while "Life is a journey" is a common metaphor in English, different cultures may conceptualize life differently, reflecting unique worldviews

(Kövecses, 2010). Cameron and Deignan (2006) further emphasized the role of metaphors in discourse, highlighting their function in education, politics, and everyday communication.

Recent studies have applied cognitive metaphor theory to various linguistic domains, including political speeches (Charteris-Black, 2004), advertising (Forceville, 2008), and second language acquisition (Littlemore, 2009). These works demonstrate the versatility of conceptual metaphors as analytical tools across diverse contexts.

Methodology. This study is based on qualitative analysis of academic literature and selected examples from authentic English texts, including media discourse, political speeches, and everyday communication. The research employed the following steps: 1) Identification of common conceptual metaphors in English (e.g., “Argument is war”, “Happiness is up”); 2) Analysis of their linguistic realizations through lexical and syntactic structures; 3) Examination of cultural and communicative functions in discourse; 4) By synthesizing theoretical perspectives and practical examples, the study seeks to demonstrate how cognitive linguistics enhances our understanding of English metaphorical language.

Results and Discussion. The analysis revealed several key contributions of cognitive linguistics to the study of conceptual metaphors:

1. Classification of metaphors. Cognitive linguistics allows for systematic categorization of metaphors into structural, orientational, and ontological types (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). For example, orientational metaphors such as “Happiness is up” appear in phrases like “I’m feeling up,” while ontological metaphors conceptualize abstract entities as objects, as in “inflation is eating up our savings.”

2. Cultural dimension. Metaphors reflect cultural values and collective experiences. For instance, the metaphor “Argument is war” is prominent in English, seen in expressions like “He shot down my argument.” However, in some Eastern cultures, arguments may be conceptualized more as negotiations or collaborative processes, reflecting different cultural attitudes toward conflict.

3. Discourse functions. Metaphors play a crucial role in persuasive communication. Political discourse frequently employs metaphors to frame complex issues in familiar terms. For example, the metaphor “Nation is a family” appears in expressions like “founding fathers” or “protecting our homeland,” appealing to emotions and shared values.

4. Pedagogical applications. In language teaching, awareness of conceptual metaphors helps learners understand idiomatic expressions and figurative meanings. Studies show that explicit instruction in metaphorical thinking improves vocabulary retention and cultural competence (Boers, 2000). Teachers can use metaphor analysis as a tool to foster critical thinking and enhance learners’ ability to interpret figurative language.

These findings suggest that conceptual metaphor theory offers a powerful interdisciplinary approach, connecting linguistics with psychology, culture, and education.

Conclusion. Cognitive linguistics, through the study of conceptual metaphors, provides valuable insights into how humans structure thought and communication. The analysis shows that metaphors are not mere ornaments of speech but essential components of cognition that reveal cultural worldviews and shape discourse. For English language studies, this approach is particularly fruitful, as it enables a deeper understanding of idiomatic expressions, rhetorical strategies, and cultural values embedded in language.

The pedagogical implications highlight the necessity of incorporating metaphor awareness into English language teaching, as it enhances learners’ comprehension of figurative meaning and cross-cultural communication. Overall, conceptual metaphor theory demonstrates the potential of cognitive linguistics to enrich both theoretical research and practical applications in the study of the English language.

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THE USE OF METAPHORS IN CONTEMPORARY ENGLISH POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract. Metaphors play a central role in shaping political communication, as they allow politicians to frame complex issues in ways that resonate with public opinion. This article explores the use of metaphors in contemporary English political discourse, focusing on speeches, debates, and media coverage from the past two decades. The study identifies the most frequent metaphorical domains – war, journey, family, and economy – and analyzes their persuasive functions. The results show that metaphors not only facilitate comprehension but also serve as tools of persuasion, ideology, and identity construction.

Keywords: metaphor, political discourse, cognitive linguistics, persuasion, ideology.

Introduction. Political discourse is not merely a matter of transmitting information but also of framing, persuasion, and identity construction. Language is central to politics, and within language, metaphors are particularly powerful. They help politicians present complex social, economic, and international issues in ways that align with ideological goals and appeal to public emotions. In contemporary English political discourse, metaphors structure debates on war, migration, economics, and national identity. Lakoff and Johnson’s (1980) theory of conceptual metaphor laid the foundation for understanding metaphors as cognitive tools, not just stylistic devices. According to their framework, metaphors shape how people think about abstract concepts by mapping them onto more concrete domains. This article applies cognitive linguistic theory to analyze the prevalence and function of metaphors in English political discourse, illustrating how they both reflect and construct political realities.

Literature Review. The study of metaphors in political communication has expanded significantly in recent decades. Charteris-Black (2005) argued that political metaphors are key instruments of legitimization, allowing politicians to frame their policies as natural or

necessary. Musolff (2016) explored the “body politic” and “family” metaphors, showing their persistence across cultures.

In the context of English-speaking countries, especially the UK and USA, metaphors of war and journey are particularly prominent. For example, war metaphors have been widely used in campaigns against poverty (“the war on poverty”), drugs (“the war on drugs”), and, more recently, COVID-19. Charteris-Black (2011) emphasized that such metaphors mobilize collective effort but also polarize society.

Cognitive linguistics provides a useful lens for analyzing these patterns. Lakoff (1991) noted how political ideologies are often built upon metaphorical conceptualizations, such as the “nation as a family.” Semino (2008) extended this to media discourse, demonstrating how journalists adopt and reinforce metaphorical framings.

Methodology. The research adopts a qualitative discourse-analytic approach. Data sources include selected political speeches, debates in the British Parliament and the US Congress, and media coverage from 2000-2023. The analysis follows these steps: identification of metaphorical expressions; categorization of metaphors according to conceptual domains (war, journey, family, economy); interpretation of pragmatic functions, such as persuasion, legitimation, and identity construction; this approach highlights both the frequency of metaphors and their ideological significance in political discourse.

Results and Discussion. The analysis reveals four dominant metaphorical domains in contemporary English political discourse:

1. War Metaphors. Politicians frequently use war metaphors to frame social and economic issues as battles that require unity and sacrifice. Phrases such as “fighting climate change” or “the war on terror” create urgency and justify extraordinary measures. These metaphors mobilize action but may oversimplify complex problems.

2. Journey Metaphors. Political progress is often framed as a collective journey, with metaphors such as “moving forward,” “the road ahead,” or “a path to recovery.” This framing emphasizes progress, continuity, and shared purpose, appealing to optimism and perseverance.

3. Family Metaphors. Leaders often refer to the nation as a family, emphasizing care, protection, and responsibility. Terms such as “our national family” or “protecting our children’s future” personalize political issues, making them emotionally accessible. However, such metaphors can also reinforce hierarchical and paternalistic ideologies.

4. Economic Metaphors. The economy is conceptualized through metaphors of health (“a sick economy,” “economic recovery”) and machinery (“the engine of growth,” “gears of the market”). These metaphors simplify abstract economic processes and help justify policy measures, but they may obscure underlying complexities.

While metaphors facilitate comprehension, they also constrain thought by framing issues in particular ways. For example, framing immigration as a “flood” or “invasion” carries negative connotations that influence public attitudes. Thus, metaphors are not neutral but ideological tools.

Conclusion. Metaphors are indispensable in contemporary English political discourse. They enable politicians to simplify complex issues, evoke emotions, and mobilize collective action. However, their power also lies in shaping thought and guiding public opinion along specific ideological lines. Understanding the use of metaphors is therefore crucial for critical engagement with political communication.

Future research should focus on cross-cultural comparisons and the role of digital media in amplifying metaphorical framings. For educators and students of linguistics,

metaphor analysis provides valuable insights into the interplay between language, cognition, and power in political life.

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PARAFRAZALARNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola parafrazalar, ularning xususiyatlari, oʻzbek tilida tutgan oʻrni, oʻzbek tilining taraqqiy etishidagi ishtiroki hamda parafrazalarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlarini, olimlarning tadqiqot natijalari va izlanishlar tahlillarini yoritib beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar. Parafraza, omonim parafraza, obrazli, uslubshunoslik, stilistik vosita, lingvokulturologiya, metafora, metonomiya, sinekdoxa.

Annotation. This article highlights paraphrases, their characteristics, their role in the Uzbek language, their contribution to the development of the Uzbek language, as well as the linguoculturological features of paraphrases. It also discusses the findings and analyses of scholars' research and investigations on the topic.

Keywords: paraphrase, homonymous paraphrase, figurative, stylistics, stylistic device, linguoculturology, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche.

Til kommunikativ aloqa vositasi sifatida insonlar orasida muloqot jarayonida ishtirok etadi. Shuning bilan birgalikda, madaniyat koʻzgusi hisoblanadi. Unda nafaqat insonni oʻrab turgan borliq, undagi xalqning ijtimoiy hayotini, uning mentalitetini, milliy xarakterini, madaniy anʼanalarini, urf-odat qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi. Til madaniyat xazinasini hisoblanib, leksika, grammatika, iboralar, maqollar, badiiy va ilmiy adabiyotlar orqali boyiydi.

Parafrazalarlar biror narsa hodisaga oʻxshatish orqali tasvirlab ifodalaydi, hamda narsa va hodisaning ikkinchi nomi hisoblanadi. Parafrazalar soʻzning maʼnosini oydinlashtirish, matnni badiiylashtirish, takronni oldini olish kabi uslubiy vazifalarni bajaradi. Oʻzbek tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalarning maʼno-mazmunini ifodalab berish, uning mohiyatini ochib berishi va qaysi uslubda qoʻllanishi uslubshunoslikning asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Parafraza atamasining xorijiy lugʻatlarda turlicha talqini uning farqli va oʻxshash tomonlari xususida bahs yuritilgan. Parafraza aslida “grekcha” soʻz boʻlib (paraphrasis),

lingvistikada jumladan, o‘zbek tilshunosligida “tasviriy ifoda “ ma’nosida qo‘llanadi. Bu hodisalar hozirgi kunda ham olimlar nazarida chetda qolgan emas. O‘rganilgan manbalarga xronologik nazar solamiz. Leksikograf olim O.S. Axmanova tahriri ostida nashr qilingan lingvistik qomusiy lug‘atda parafrazaga “biror so‘zni ba‘zi predmetlarning so‘zlar orqali oddiy ifodalanishini tasviriy ifoda bilan almashtirishdan iborat bo‘lgan ko‘chim” deb izoh bergan.[1, 312-b] O‘zbek tilshunosligida ko‘chim turi sifatida parafrazani o‘quv qo‘llanmalariga olib kirgan tilshunos olim R.Qo‘ng‘urov 1893-yilda nashr etilgan “O‘zbek tili stilistikasi” qo‘llanmasida: “...kishilarning otlarini yoki boshqa predmetlarning nomini to‘g‘ridan to‘g‘ri gapirmasdan, ularni turli xil so‘z yoki tasviriy ifodalarda vositasida bayon qilish perifrastik deyiladi” deb ta’rif bergan [4, 148-b]. Tasviriy ifodalarning parafrastik yoki perifrastik, parafrastik, perifrastik deb yuritiladigan nomlari bir xil ma’noni anglatadi. Bu borada tadqiqot olib borgan tilshunos olimlardan. M.Mirtojiyevning tadqiqotlarida batafsilroq o‘rganilgan.Olimlarning ta’kidlashicha “parafrastiklar ma’lum bo‘lak yoki ko‘chma ma’noda bo‘lib, ular ma’nosi sintezidan tashkil topgan, bir tushunchani bildiruvchi lug‘aviy birliklardir...

Parafrastiklar haqida shu kungacha ko‘plab maqolalar va disertatsiyalar ishlangan. Bundan avval parafrastiklar maxsus ilmiy tadqiqot obyekti sifatida rejada o‘rganilmagan. Shuningdek, parafrastiklar badiiy tasvir vositalaridan biri sifatida og‘zaki nutqimizda ham yozma nutqimizda ham keng qo‘llanadi. Parafrastiklar tilimizning naqadar boyligi hamda ta’sirchan ekanligini ham ko‘rsatadi. Ularning shaxs-narsa, buyum, voqea-hodisalarni tasvirlash yo‘li bilan so‘z birikmalari holida ifodalaydigan birikmalarga yoki so‘zga tasviriy ifodalari yoki parafrastiklar deb yuritiladi.

Parafrastiklar holida maqom olgan birikmada, garchi semantik qayta bo‘linish kuzatilmaydi”[2,67-b]. Parafrastiklar omonim, sinonim hamda metafora, metonimiya va sinekdoxa kabi ma’noviy shakllari mavjuddir. Omonim parafrastiklar nutqimizda bir parafrastiklar o‘rnida qo‘llanilsa, unda bular shakldosh parafrastiklar. Masalan, Aql gimnastikasi- shahmat, matematika Qora oltin- neft va ko‘mir Bahor elchisi- qaldirg‘och va deyiladi boychechak kabilar Sinonim parafrastiklar esa bir so‘zning bir necha tasviriy ifodalari bo‘lsa ular ma’nodosh hisoblanadi. Masalan, Televizor-zangori ekran, oynayi jahon Bahor-fasllar kelinchagi, uyg‘onish fasli kabi. Metafora asosida ma’no ko‘chishida parafrastiklar – muayyan hodisa va belgilarning nomini boshqasiga o‘zaro tashqi o‘xshashlik asosida ko‘chirish jarayonidir. Metafora asosida o‘xshashlik asosan uning rangi va xususiyatining o‘xshashligi yetakchilik qiladi. Misol qilib olsak, qora oltin-neft, oq oltin-paxta, zangori olov-gaz, yashil boylik-ormon kabi. Metonimiya asosida o‘xshashlikda bunda biror narsa hodisaning nomi bir narsaga o‘xshashlik asosida emas, balki o‘zaro bog‘liqlik asosida ko‘chishidir. Qiyoslaymiz, Alisher Navoiy-g‘azal mulkingning sultoni, Abdulla Qodiriy-o‘zbek romanchiliging asoschisi yoki paxtakorlar- oq oltin ijodkorlari. Demak, metonimiyadagi predmetlararo bog‘liqlik parafrastiklarga ham xosdir. Biroq parafrastiklardagi o‘xshashlik o‘zaro bog‘liqlik tasviriy - obrazli holatda bo‘ladi. Obrazli parafrastiklarga biror predmetni unga taalluqli bo‘lgan o‘xshashlik bilan tasvirlashdir. Bunga misol qilib “oq oltin”, “zangori ekran”, “kumush tola”, “oq chashma”, “zangori olov” kabi.

Sinekdoxa usulida parafrastiklarning o‘xshashligi, bunda butun orqali qism tasvirlanadi. Professor olim SH.Rahmatullayev sinekdoxani “bir predmetning nomi boshqa bir predmetga qism bilan butun munosabatining aks etishi” dir deb ta’riflaydi. Misol qilib oladigan bo‘lsak, peshonasi sho‘r, zangori ekran, kumush tola kabi.

Parafrastiklar haqida qarashlar qadim zamonlardan mavjud bo‘lgan shuningdek, bu haqida qadimgi til va uslubi nazariyotchilaridan Aristotel va Kvintilian tomonidan qayd

etilganligi, mahalliy va sharqiy slavyan tilshunosligining ham diqqat markazida turganligi manbalarda qayd etilgan [5].

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O‘ZBEK TILI TARAQQIYOTIDA YUZAGA KELAYOTGAN LINGVISTIK MUAMMOLAR

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Annatsiya: O‘zbek tilshunosligining bugungi kundagi dolzarb muammolari, ularni yuzaga keltirayotgan ijtimoiy, texnologik va madaniy omillar chuqur tahlil etiladi. Xususan, yoshlar orasida adabiy til me‘yorlariga amal qilinmasligi, so‘z boyligining qisqarishi, inglizcha va ruscha so‘zlarning ortiqcha qo‘llanishi, til va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi uzviy bog‘liqlik muammosi sifatida ko‘rsatib o‘tiladi. Tilga aralashuv hodisasi “lingvistik aralashuv” sifatida baholanib, uning salbiy oqibatlari yoritiladi. Matnda, shuningdek, yangi fan-texnika yutuqlari, raqamli texnologiyalar va sun‘iy intellekt bilan bog‘liq tilshunoslikning yangi yo‘nalishlari – lingvopragmatika, psixolingvistika, kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi va boshqalar haqida ma‘lumot beriladi. Muammoni hal qilish yo‘llari sifatida ona tilini targ‘ib qilish, adabiy tilni ommalashtirish, maktab va internetda adabiy tildan foydalanishni kuchaytirish taklif etiladi. Matnda, shuningdek, an‘anaviy va zamonaviy tilshunoslik muammolari farqlanib, hozirgi o‘zbek tilshunosligining vazifalari va istiqbollari belgilab beriladi. Oliy ta‘limda fanlararo yondashuv va tizimli tahlil orqali nazariy bilimlarni chuqurlashtirish zarurligi alohida ta‘kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlari: o‘zbek tilshunosligi, dolzarb muammolar, lingvistik aralashuv, adabiy til, so‘z boyligi, terminlar tarjimai, sun‘iy intellekt, kompyuter lingvistikasi, lingvopragmatika, psixolingvistika, til va jamiyat, oliy ta‘lim, fanlararo yondashuv, raqamli texnologiyalar, tizimli tahlil.

Bugungi yoshlar orasida til odobi me‘yorlarining buzilishi, so‘z boyligining qisqarishi, o‘zbek tiliga inglizcha va ruscha so‘zlarning haddan ziyod qo‘llanishi kuzatilmoqda. Bu holat tilni o‘zligidan ayirish xavfini tug‘dirmoqda. Tilshunoslikda bu muammo “lingvistik aralashuv” deb yuritiladi. O‘zbek tilining adabiy tili bilan turli hududiy dialektlar (qashqadaryo, farg‘ona, buxoro, xorazm va b.) o‘rtasidagi farq tobora kuchaymoqda. Ko‘plab yoshlar adabiy til me‘yorlarini o‘zlashtirishda qiynalishmoqda. Yangi fan-texnika yutuqlari tufayli yangi so‘zlar paydo bo‘lmoqda. Ammo bu so‘zlar o‘zbek tiliga to‘g‘ri tarjima

qilinmayapti yoki umuman tarjima qilinmasdan qo‘llanmoqda. Bu esa til boyligiga salbiy ta‘sir qiladi. Tilshunoslikdagi dolzarb muammolar – bu nafaqat lingvistik masalalar, balki jamiyat taraqqiyoti, ma‘naviy yuksalish, madaniyat va siyosat bilan uzviy bog‘liq muammolardir. Bu muammolarning yechimi uchun:

- Ona tilining targ‘ibotini kuchaytirish;
- Adabiy tilni ommalashtirish;
- Terminlarni o‘zbek tiliga moslashtirish;
- Internetda adabiy tilda yozilgan kontentni ko‘paytirish;
- Maktablarda so‘z boyligini oshirishga qaratilgan darslarni ko‘paytirish kabi chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirish zarur.

Til – millatning yuragi, uni asrash esa har bir fuqaroning burchidir. O‘zbek tilining an‘anaviy tilshunosligi zaminida shakllangan, taraqqiyot yo‘lini tanlagan va belgilangan maqsad asosidagi vazifalarini muvaffaqiyatli ado etgan o‘zbek tilshunosligining hozirgi holati yangi yo‘nalishlarning shakllanishini taqozo qilmoqda. Ular diqqat-markazida lison-nutq masalasini turli daraja va ko‘rinishda namoyon qiluvchi til va jamiyat, til va madaniyat, til va shaxs, milliy til va milliy tafakkur, til va sun‘iy intellekt kabi substansial asoslarda hal qilinuvchi muammolar turadi. Jahon tilshunosligida XX asr so‘ngida shakllanib, jadal rivojlanayotgan fanning yangi paradigmalari lingvopragmatika, psixolingvistika, lingvokulturologiya, lingvokognitologiya, kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi kabi ilg‘or fan yo‘nalishlari aynan shu masalalar tadqiqi bilan shug‘ullanmoqda. Istiqbol natijasi o‘laroq, o‘zbek tilshunosligi tom ma‘noda mustaqil milliy fan sifatida o‘zini namoyon qildi. Eng muhimi, tilimizning milliy tabiatiga to‘laqonli ilmiy nazariy baho berildi. Qo‘lga kiritilgan nazariy yutuqlar til qurilishini o‘rganishdan uning voqelanish xususiyatlarining keng qamrovli tadqiqiga o‘tish uchun katta imkoniyatdir. Bu esa o‘zbek tilini yangi va zamonaviy, ilg‘or va samarador tadqiq usullari asosida tekshirishni kun tartibiga qo‘ymoqda. Bugungi kunda tilshunoslikning ayrim juz‘iy muammolariga dolzarblik tusi berilayotgani holda, mavjud ilmiy salohiyat muhim muammolar echimiga yo‘naltirilmayapti, sohaning istiqbolini belgilaydigan asosiy vazifalar hamon kun tartibidan chetda qolmoqda. Shuning uchun ushbu kursda o‘zbek tilshunosligining yangi asrda hal etilishi lozim bo‘lgan, to‘la ma‘noda dolzarb muammolari haqida so‘z boradi. Tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari kishilik jamiyatining amaliy ehtiyojlari ta‘sirida yuzaga kelgan tilshunoslikning mustaqil bir sohasidir. Kishilik jamiyatining taraqqiy eta borishida O‘zbek tilshunosligining dolzarb muammolari yechishi lozim bo‘lgan masalalari ham, shu masalalarni hal qilishga yo‘naltirilgan yo‘l yo‘riqlari va metodlari ham o‘zib, rivojlanib boradi. Bu muammolarni an‘anaviy hamda yangi muammolarga ajratish mumkin. An‘anaviy muammolar qatoriga tilshunoslik tomonidan asrlar davomida yechib kelingan, lison hamda nutq hodisalarini imkoniyat doirasida tadqiqi va hamisha jamiyatning o‘quv-o‘qituv ishlarini talab darajasida tashkil etishga yo‘naltirilgan amaliy ishlarni kiritish mumkin. Yangi muammolar qatorida quyidagilarni sanash mumkin: mashinaviy tarjimaning lingvistik asoslarini yaratish, informatsion tillar va ularning inson tabiiy tiliga munosabati, terminologiyasi va uning axborot izlashga munosabati, hujjatlarni avtomatik indekslashtirish, hujjatlarni avtomatik tarzda referatlash va annotatsiyalash, axborot tizimi ishlarini lingvistik jihatdan ta‘minlash, avtomatik axborot izlash uchun lug‘at tuzish, matnni avtomatik sintezlash va lisonning nutqiy voqelanishining mukammal tadqiqi kabilar. O‘zbek nomli etnosotsial jamoa, ya‘ni millatga taalluqli, uning boy tarixini o‘zida aks ettiruvchi, kundalik aloqa-muloqat ehtiyojini to‘lato‘kis qondiruvchi, uni birlashtiruvchi, jipslashtiruvchi o‘zbek tilining tabiatini, shakllanish, taraqqiy topish bosqichlari kechagi va bugungi holati, ertangi istiqboli xususida aniq hamda ravshan tasavvurga ega o‘zbek tilshunosligi uchun hozirgi zamon jahon

tilshunosligida yuz berayotgan o'zgarishlar yot emas. Hech ikkilanmay ta'kidlash lozimki, o'zbek tili tizimida nafaqat qardosh turkiy tillarga oid xususiy jihatlar, shuningdek dunyoning besh qit'asida mavjud mustaqil tillarga doir umumiy qonuniyatlar ham qaror topgan. Shu nuqtayi nazardan o'zbek tilshunosligi bosib o'tgan murakkab yo'lga ilmiy yondashishda, obyektiv baho berishda unga xos qonuniyatlarni umumlingvistik hodisalar, jarayonlardan ajratib qo'ymaslik yoki yulib olmaslik talab qilinadi. O'zbek tilshunosligi so'nggi yillar davomida ma'lum darajada o'sib, taraqqiyot ta'sirida paydo bo'layotgan masalalarni hal etishga diqqatini qaratish, Jahon tilshunosligidagi singari o'zbek tilshunosligida ham endilikda e'tibor til strukturasi muammosidan tilning inson faoliyatining turli sohalaridagi vazifasiga ko'cha boshladi. Tilning sistem xarakteri, til birliklarining paradigmatic va sintagmatic xususiyatlari, o'zaro munosabatini atroflicha tahlil etish kun tartibidan barqaror joy oldi. Bugun zamonaviy jahon tilshunosligidan muhim o'rin olayotgan jihat bu inson faoliyatining turli sohalar bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lgan ilmiy ma'lumotlar singishi va o'zaro ta'siri hisoblanadi. Lingvistikaning turli fan sohalar bilan munosabatga kirishi natijasida tilshunoslikda etnolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, matematik lingvistika, kompyuter tilshunosligi kabi paydo bo'lgan yangi yo'nalishlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari haqida talabalarga puxta bilim berish, yosh iste'dodlarni mazkur sohalariga dadil yo'llash berish lozim. Bugun oliy o'quv maskanlarida o'zbek tilini o'qitish jarayonida unga tizim sifatida yondashish, tizim qonuniyatlari negizida til va uning birliklari hamda hodisalarini talqin etish, shakl va mazmun asimmetriyasi, ona tilning funksional ko'pqirraligi haqida chuqur ilm berish, nazariy jihatdan yirik lingvistlar tayyorlashda tarixiy tilshunoslik tutgan mavqeini aniq belgilash zarur. Oliy ta'lim tizimini tashkil etishning ustuvor vazifalaridan biri tarzida talaba bilimining sintezi, fanlararo aloqa omilining e'tirof etilishidir.

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LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES AND ACTUAL ISSUES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: Linguistics plays a vital role in comprehending the form, function and evolution of language. In the age of globalization, linguistic research encounters new difficulties concerning linguistic conservation, normalisation, translation, and digitalization. This article explores the most significant issues in modern linguistics, including linguistic policy, the influence of global integration, the impact of digital technologies, and the incorporation of artificial intelligence. A methodical approach for resolving these challenges – integrating theoretical linguistics, practical research, language planning, and technological advancement – is suggested.

Key Words: linguistic challenges, language policy, standardization, translation, digitalization, globalization, artificial intelligence, language preservation, language planning.

Language is not only a channel of human interaction but also an influential tool for preserving cultural heritage, historical experience and identity. In our digital connected age, languages are witnessing rapid evolution driven by digital progress, human migration, and cultural exchange. In many societies, saving the native language is seen as essential, while in others, the central point is on language management and modernization [1].

Today's linguistic science explores beyond traditional domains – phonetics, morphology, syntax, and semantics – to analyze how language connects with digital platforms, worldwide communication system and artificial intelligence. These new contexts have evolved linguistic studies more cross-disciplinary and socially meaningful [2].

Across the globe, countless minority languages are facing the danger of language disappearance. The decline of a language signifies the fading of cultural heritage, traditions and people's memory. Linguistic experts are confronted with the difficulty of archiving threatened languages, designing digital corpora and development.

Through the global interconnection, a limited number of world languages have gained supremacy, which has marginalized and endangered smaller linguistic communities. Defining language standards, the maintenance of literary norms and the support of linguistic plurality are vital importance for linguistic development. Effective language management and policy play a crucial role in protecting equilibrium between national and international communication.

Among the many branches of practical linguistics, translation remains a vibrant and constantly evolving field. As intercultural communication develops, professional translation becomes essential. The main difficulties involve accurately rendering cultural meanings, idiomatic phrases, and stylistic details [3].

The technological age has completely transformed the ways in which languages are practiced and communicated. Social networks, technological platforms, and virtual communication have contributed to numerous neologisms, shortened forms, and blended expressions. The science of language should systematically study current transformations and purpose strategies to protect the consistency of language.

The adoption of AI technologies in linguistic research has generated both new possibilities and complex issues. Automated translation, speech recognition, AI-based text generation, and linguistic modeling are rapidly evolving fields. Language researchers have to collaborate with technology specialist to guarantee the correct modeling linguistic patterns in AI systems.

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INTEGRATING JEAN PIAGET'S COGNITIVE THEORY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article explores Jean Piaget's cognitive development theory and its theoretical as well as practical significance in language education. According to Piaget, the process of knowledge acquisition in learners develops step by step, and cognitive development plays a crucial role in their educational activities. Applying this theory in language teaching allows educators to select methods based on learners' age characteristics and to implement effective pedagogical strategies. The study analyzes the advantages of a cognitive approach in language teaching and enriches theoretical conclusions with practical recommendations. The results of the article are of great scientific and practical importance for shaping innovative approaches in modern education.

Keywords: Jean Piaget, cognitive theory, language education, teaching methods, cognitive development.

In today's era of globalization and digitalization, the importance of innovative approaches in language education is increasing. In particular, methods aimed at developing students' thinking processes, cognitive activity, and effective assimilation of knowledge are gaining particular relevance in modern education. Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development is distinguished by its scientific justification of the gradual acquisition of knowledge by students. The methods and strategies used in the educational process based on this theory are effective not only in language teaching, but also in developing students' independent thinking, problem-solving, and communicative skills. The main purpose of this study is to analyze the theoretical and practical aspects of the approach based on Jean Piaget's cognitive theory in language education and to highlight its importance in the modern educational process.

Jean Piaget carved out his own niche in a discipline that he called genetic epistemology, the study of how intelligence changes as children grow. Piaget was not interested in comparing levels of intelligence between children of different ages (quantitative cognitive change); his interests lay in the natural development of mental skills over time (qualitative cognitive change).[1.3p]

Piaget grouped cognitive development into four stages. Piaget's stages are like steps, each building on the one before it, helping children to build their understanding of the world.

The four stages are:

1. Sensorimotor: birth to 2 years
2. Preoperational: ages 2 to 7
3. Concrete operational: ages 7 to 11
4. Formal operational: ages 12 and up.

1. At the sensorimotor stage, babies learn about the world through touch and their other senses.
2. Children begin to arrange objects logically during the pre-operational stage.
3. During the concrete operational stage, children learn that quantities can take different forms.
4. Verbal reasoning and hypothetical thinking develop in the formal operational stage.

While developing the cognitive theory, Piaget made some assumptions about children which include:

- 1) Based on their experiences, children build their knowledge,
- 2) Children learn things without influence from others,
- 3) By nature, children are motivated to learn. The four basic elements in cognitive development are maturation, experience, social transmission and equilibrium. Piaget's clinical method is a research technique used to investigate children's cognitive development. It is a research approach for understanding children's thinking that Piaget adapted from the diagnostic clinical interview used in psychopathology.

Unlike standardized tests, the clinical method uses flexible, open-ended questions to explore the child's thinking in depth. The interviewer adapts their questions based on the child's initial responses, prompting further explanation and clarification. Findings from two major branches of cognitive science have been particularly influential: cognitive psychology, which relies on interpretive, behavioral, and observational methodologies, and cognitive neuroscience, which is grounded in neuroimaging techniques. Numerous theories of effective learning have emerged from research in these :

1. Spaced learning - distributing learning and retrieval opportunities over a longer period of time rather than concentrating them in 'massed' practice;
2. Interleaving - switching between different types of problem or different ideas within the same lesson or study session;
3. Retrieval practice - using a variety of strategies to recall information from memory, for example flash cards, practice tests or quizzing, or mind-map ping;
4. Strategies to manage cognitive load - focusing students on key information without overloading them, for example, by breaking down or 'chunking' subject content or using worked examples, exemplars, or 'scaffolds'; and
5. Dual coding - using both verbal and non-verbal information (such as words and pictures) to teach concepts; dual coding forms one part of a wider theory known as the cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML).

Cognitive science principles of learning can have a real impact on rates of learning in the classroom. There is value in teachers having working knowledge of cognitive science principles. There are several advantages and limitations to the cognitive approach. One strength of the cognitive approach is that it has many practical applications. For example, Baron-Cohen et al's study demonstrated how theory of mind was a deficit of autism and provided a new test for Theory of mind. The test could then be used again to help determine if somebody has autism, whilst the knowledge that people with autism or Asperger's syndrome lack theory of mind can help us better understand what autism consists of and how to accommodate this into school or work situations. Studies such as Loftus and Palmer's experiment into leading questions have also greatly impacted forensic psychology and

eyewitness testimony. Therefore, this is a very useful approach with many contributions to psychology and society as a whole.

The main disadvantage of the cognitive approach is that it refers to cognitive processes that we cannot directly observe. It relies heavily on inference. Critics of Loftus and Palmer's leading questions experiments pointed to the validity of the re constructive memory hypothesis, as we cannot be sure that memory has changed as the researchers couldn't observe memories, but only the answers given - which may have been the result of demand characteristics, or even poor judgement of speed. Therefore, the cognitive approach may lack being scientific on the basis that it is subjective in what is taken from findings. Assuming that findings are the result of invisible processes is heavily subjective and could lead to self-fulfilling prophecy and internal validity being raised as issues.

Jean Piaget's theory is one of the most influential theories in developmental psychology. It outlines how children actively construct knowledge as they explore and interact with the world around them. Piaget's ideas have had a huge impact on teaching, particularly at primary level, and his analysis of how we learn has influenced the way teachers and schools structure the curriculum and deliver content. Piaget proposed that problem-solving and logical processing skills are required for new learning to occur. Therefore the teacher needs to be a facilitator within the classroom and support pupils through the adaptation process, rather than merely feed them information.

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THE LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SCIENTIFIC ENGLISH: STANDARDIZATION AND VARIATION

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Annotation: This paper examines the linguistic features of scientific English as the main medium of global academic communication. It analyzes how standardization promotes clarity and objectivity, while variation reflects disciplinary and multilingual diversity. The study highlights lexical, grammatical, and stylistic traits of modern scientific discourse, concluding that English remains both unifying and adaptable across cultural contexts.

Keywords: scientific English, linguistics, standardization, variation, academic discourse, globalization, stylistic features, English as a lingua franca

In recent decades, the English language has gained the status of the dominant medium of international scientific communication. The rapid growth of global academic exchange,

digital publication platforms, and international collaboration has made scientific English not only a practical necessity but also a linguistic phenomenon worthy of deeper study. Unlike general English, scientific English demonstrates a unique set of lexical, grammatical, and stylistic norms that reflect the need for precision, neutrality, and universality in academic discourse [1, p. 42].

The investigation of linguistic features of scientific English is especially relevant today, as the academic community faces the challenge of balancing standardization with the natural variation brought by non-native contributors and disciplinary differences. Understanding these linguistic mechanisms is crucial for ensuring accessibility and maintaining the quality of international research communication.

One of the most significant characteristics of scientific English is its specialized vocabulary. Scientific terms often emerge through processes of borrowing, derivation, and compounding, forming a distinct lexical layer that differentiates academic discourse from general usage [2, p. 118]. Terms such as *photosynthesis*, *neurotransmission*, and *nanostructure* are examples of how linguistic economy and semantic precision function within this register.

Scientific English also favors nominalization – the transformation of verbs and adjectives into nouns – which allows for a more abstract and objective style (e.g., *analyze* → *analysis*; *strong* → *strength*). This tendency minimizes personal involvement and creates a formal, detached tone. However, linguistic variation occurs across disciplines: humanities papers often include more evaluative and metaphorical language, while technical sciences emphasize terminological accuracy [3, p. 67].

At the grammatical level, scientific English is characterized by complex sentence structures, frequent use of the passive voice, and logical cohesion. The passive voice (“*was conducted*,” “*was observed*”) serves to focus on processes and results rather than on the researcher, thus supporting objectivity [8, p. 91]. Cohesive devices such as *therefore*, *however*, and *in addition* are essential for building logical argumentation.

Nevertheless, recent studies show a gradual shift toward more reader-friendly syntax, especially in interdisciplinary and open-access publications [4, p. 54]. Shorter sentences and active constructions are increasingly accepted, reflecting a trend toward communicative efficiency and accessibility in global academia.

Stylistically, scientific English strives for clarity, conciseness, and accuracy. Redundant expressions and emotional tone are avoided. Yet, scientific texts differ in tone and structure depending on the discipline and publication type. For instance, linguistics and social sciences may tolerate a degree of subjectivity and interpretation, whereas natural sciences demand rigorous precision and replicability [9, p. 32].

The functional role of standardization lies in maintaining shared communicative norms, enabling scientists from diverse backgrounds to exchange knowledge effectively. Variation reflects the ongoing influence of multilingual authorship and cross-cultural perspectives. As researchers from non-English-speaking countries contribute to the global academic dialogue, they introduce subtle lexical and syntactic variations that enrich scientific discourse [5, p. 28].

The globalization of research has transformed English into the central medium of academic communication, creating a need for a standardized linguistic model that ensures clarity and accessibility for the international scientific community. Standardization in scientific English refers to the establishment of consistent lexical, grammatical, and stylistic norms that facilitate comprehension regardless of cultural or linguistic background [3, p. 77]. These norms are reinforced through international editorial policies, peer review practices, and

style manuals such as the *APA* or *Chicago Manual of Style*. Standardization thus serves as a form of linguistic codification, stabilizing the conventions of academic writing.

However, standardization does not imply complete linguistic uniformity. The emergence of English as a **lingua franca of science** has encouraged the participation of scholars from diverse linguistic and cultural contexts, leading to what Mauranen (2006) calls “*negotiated English*” – a version of English shaped by multilingual interaction rather than native norms [7, p. 104]. In this environment, variation arises naturally as non-native speakers adapt English to reflect their local academic traditions, rhetorical styles, and conceptual frameworks. Such variation does not undermine the communicative function of scientific English; on the contrary, it enriches the global academic dialogue by introducing new perspectives and terminological nuances.

Variation manifests at multiple linguistic levels. **Lexically**, scholars incorporate terminology specific to regional research traditions or transliterated concepts that lack direct equivalents in English. For instance, terms in linguistics or cultural studies often retain traces of their original linguistic identity (*Bildung*, *habitus*, *aidos*), reflecting the epistemological diversity of global science [6, p. 29]. **Syntactically**, authors from different linguistic backgrounds may prefer distinct patterns of argumentation – for example, extended hypotactic constructions typical of Slavic academic writing or more compact, paratactic styles common in Anglo-American discourse. These variations highlight how language structures not only communication but also modes of reasoning within different scholarly traditions.

Moreover, **disciplinary variation** also plays a crucial role. The conventions of scientific English are not monolithic but discipline-dependent: research articles in natural sciences prioritize precision, impersonal reporting, and standardized methods, while humanities and social sciences allow greater interpretive flexibility and evaluative language [6, p. 67]. Thus, even within standardized frameworks, scientific English accommodates a range of communicative styles shaped by epistemic goals and disciplinary epistemologies.

A further aspect of variation stems from the digital transformation of academia. The spread of open-access journals and online platforms has diversified linguistic practices, encouraging researchers to write for broader audiences. This trend promotes simpler syntax, direct sentence structures, and a semi-formal tone, reflecting the balance between scholarly rigor and accessibility in the digital age [6, p. 54].

In conclusion, Scientific English exemplifies the complex interaction between standardization and variation. While standardization establishes shared linguistic norms that make international research accessible and coherent, variation reflects the diversity of linguistic identities, disciplines, and communicative purposes in global academia. The recent rise of English as a lingua franca demonstrates that linguistic uniformity is neither possible nor desirable. Instead, the adaptability of scientific English allows it to serve as an inclusive medium that accommodates different rhetorical traditions and evolving digital communication forms.

Therefore, understanding the dynamics between standardization and variation contributes not only to linguistic theory but also to improving intercultural competence in research writing. The study of these linguistic processes helps scholars recognize English not as a monolithic standard, but as a living, evolving system shaped by the plurality of global academic voices.

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THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PHONETICS AND PHONOLOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the main differences between phonetics and phonology, two closely related branches of linguistics. It highlights how phonetics studies the physical properties of sounds, while phonology examines their functional and abstract aspects in language systems.

Keywords: phonetics, phonology, linguistics, sound system, speech, language, teachers, meaning, articulatory, acoustic.

Phonetics and phonology are two related but distinct areas of linguistics that deal with the sounds of human language. While they are often studied together, they are fundamentally different in their approach and focus. Language is one of the most important means of human communication. It consists of several structural levels that together form a complex system. Among these levels, phonetics and phonology hold a special place because they deal with the sound system of language. Although these two fields are closely connected, they differ significantly in their scope, objectives, and methods. Understanding the differences between phonetics and phonology is essential for linguists, teachers, and students alike.

Phonetics and phonology are both branches of linguistics that study sounds, yet they do so from different perspectives. Phonetics focuses on how sounds are produced, transmitted, and perceived as physical phenomena. Phonology, however, studies how those sounds function within a particular language to distinguish meaning. Phonetics is the study of the physical nature of speech sounds. It investigates how sounds are articulated by the speech organs, transmitted through the air, and perceived by the ear. The field of phonetics is divided into three main branches:

1. Articulatory phonetics – how speech sounds are produced by the human vocal tract.
2. Acoustic phonetics – how speech sounds behave as sound waves in the air.
3. Auditory phonetics – how the human ear perceives and processes sounds.

Phonology, on the other hand, studies the way sounds are organized in a particular language. Also, it is the study of the abstract sound system of a language. It examines how sounds are organized and used in language. It deals with phonemes, the smallest sound units that can change meaning. Phonology also studies the rules and patterns of sound combinations in language, such as the rules of stress and intonation. One way to illustrate the difference between phonetics and phonology is to consider the difference between a phone and a

phoneme. A phone is a physical sound produced by the human vocal apparatus, while a phoneme is an abstract unit of sound that distinguishes one word from another in a language. For example, the words “bat” and “pat” differ by one sound - /b/ and /p/ - which means that these sounds represent different phonemes in English.

Phonetics and phonology also have different goals and methods of analysis. Phonetics aims to describe and classify all possible speech sounds, including those found in non-human languages. Phonetics uses instruments such as spectrograms and electroglottographs to analyze speech sounds and measure their physical properties. Phonology, on the other hand, aims to uncover the underlying patterns and rules that govern the sound system of a language. Phonology uses tools such as phonological rules and morphophonemic analysis to describe the structure and organization of speech sounds in a language.

Another difference lies in their methodology. Phonetic studies often use experimental instruments, such as spectrograms and recording devices, to measure and visualize sound waves. Phonology uses abstract models, rules, and representations to explain patterns and relationships among sounds in a language. While phonetics describes how sounds are produced, phonology explains why they behave in a certain way within a linguistic system. In other words, phonetics concerns performance (what speakers do), whereas phonology concerns competence (what speakers know). For example, English speakers unconsciously aspirate the /p/ sound in “pin” but not in “spin”. Phonetics describes the aspiration process; phonology explains the rule behind why it occurs in some positions and not others.

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THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING THE LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract: Communities nowadays are dealing with a growing number of abrupt and significant changes as well as conflicts that impact social, political, and economic facets of daily life. In the millennial era, education's significance has also come under scrutiny. In actuality, curriculum design for 21st century learning needs to gradually change in order to emphasize the transferable skills that students must acquire in classroom environments. The kinds of abilities and competences that students must acquire in today's knowledge-based learning environment are different from those of the past. One of the most significant advancements in language teaching is the emphasis on communicative ability. Communicative activities in EFL/ESL classrooms prepare students to utilize English in other contexts, depending on their individual needs, interests, and opportunities.

Keywords: Communicative competence, communicative approach, social language, task-based language learning, text-based teaching.

English's influence and function in the globe today are expanding at an accelerated rate. The primary causes of this phenomena are the increase in the speed and scope of information transmission in the global village as well as the expansion of communication with the globe following independence. English holds a strong dominant position in the online realm when it comes to the language of published content, which is a powerful incentive for individuals looking to advance their global competences to learn the language [1].

A communicative approach is an approach which is worldwide known and established it has established itself in many parts of the world as a way of teaching languages, especially English. It is the approach that has prevailed in English Language Teaching over the past 50 years, and it is still used nowadays [2]. The origins of the Communicative Approach are to be found in the late 1960s and early 1970s. The communicative approach is the product of some linguists and educators who had grown dissatisfied with the previous two methods used for foreign language teaching; the audio-lingual method and Grammar-translation method. These great linguists and educators who contributed to the rise of this worldwide used approach are Hymes, Chomsky, Wilkins, Van Ek and Alexander, and the Council of Europe. All of these linguists and educators believed, meanwhile, that pupils at that time were not picking up the language properly. They argued that actual language and the "whole language" were not taught to them. Pupils lacked the social language skills necessary to interact with people outside of the classroom in everyday settings. Thus far, they have depended on language structures rather than language functions and concepts. As a result, they were unable to interact with others in the language's culture [3].

The method of teaching second and foreign languages known as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) places a strong emphasis on interaction as the ultimate purpose of language learning as well as its means. Another name for it is the "Communicative Approach." In the past, CLT has been viewed as both an expansion or improvement of the Notional-Functional Syllabus and a reaction to the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM). A more modern improvement on CLT called task-based language learning has seen a significant increase in popularity.

A set of guidelines about the objectives of language instruction, how language acquisition occurs, the kinds of classroom exercises that promote learning, and the roles that teachers and students should play in the classroom can be referred to as communicative language teaching.

Communicative competence includes the following aspects of language knowledge:

Knowing how to use language for a range of different purposes and functions;

Knowing how to vary our use of language according to the setting and the participants;

Knowing how to produce and understand different types of texts;

Knowing how to maintain communication despite having limitations in one's language knowledge.

The emphasis is on appropriate language use rather than accuracy. At a subsequent phase is accuracy. It's thought that correctness comes naturally to those who learn how to use the language correctly. Teaching language should involve the integration of various language skills, rather than focusing on just one. It implies that developing reading and writing skills is just as important as honing speaking abilities when it comes to communication strategies. It is impossible to learn a language by rote repetition. It is impossible to learn on its own. It ought to be acquired by social contact. One must struggle with language in order to communicate in the target language. According to Richards and Rodgers, the most effective way to learn the target language system is to struggle with communication. Making the student able to converse in the target language is the main goal when employing this method.

The teacher accepts mistakes because the main goal is to help the students become proficient speakers of the target language. When students are engaging in tasks that require them to use the target language, the teacher shouldn't correct them. The instructor can point out the mistakes made by the students and fix them. The CLT approach gives learners opportunities to communicate in the language of instruction. It promotes communication between students and between teachers. It facilitates the development of pupils' cooperative relationships. Work should be assigned by the teacher in groups or pairs so that students can exchange the material with one another. It facilitates their communication with one another as well. According to Richards and Rodgers, students are encouraged to engage with others through written work, pair and group projects, and in-person interactions. The CLT technique gives students the chance to practice saying things correctly as well as what to say. It is the teacher's responsibility to set up scenarios that facilitate communication. They should learn from the teacher how to utilize language in a social setting. The instructor must to include exercises like role-playing that aid students in acquiring the language in a social setting. Techniques for teaching languages should be created in a way that motivates students to utilize the target language. Language's functional elements ought to be prioritized. To encourage genuine communication in the classroom, employ role plays, dramas, and games. It is important to provide students with opportunity to hear language in natural settings. They might receive coaching on techniques to increase their comprehension. [8] As previously outlined, CLT can now be seen as describing a collection of fundamental assumptions about language learning and teaching, assumptions that may be used in various contexts and that touch on various facets of the teaching and learning processes. Some place a strong emphasis on the input into the process of learning. Thus, content-based education emphasizes that the entire process of learning a language is driven by the subject matter being taught. Certain teaching proposals place a greater emphasis on the processes of instruction. For instance, task-based training promotes using specifically created instructional tasks as the cornerstone of learning. Some emphasize learning outcomes and employ results or products as the foundation for lesson preparation, such as competency-based education and text-based teaching.

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THE DIFFERENCE OF THE WORD ORDER OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Comparative typology helps to compare languages through their grammatical structures. Among these, word order is a central feature that shows how Uzbek and English differ in their typological systems. Understanding word order typology is essential for linguists as it helps in comparative studies of languages. This study explores the typological features of word order in Uzbek and English languages. Word order plays a crucial role in expressing grammatical relations and sentence meaning. The study identifies similarities and differences between the two languages and shows their effects in sentences.

Key words: comparative typology, linguistic typology, Uzbek and English languages, typological features, word order, grammar rules, subject, object, verb.

Linguistic typology is the study of language by classifying and comparing languages based on their structural and grammatical features, such as word order, morphology, and phonology. **Comparative typology** is one of the independent branches of linguistic typology. It compares at least two languages. In today's world, word order is one of the main systems of communication for Uzbek and English speakers. **Word order typology** influences sentence structure by providing a framework for how different languages organize subjects, verbs, and objects [5, p. 45]. For example, languages that follow an SVO pattern place the subject before the verb and object, while SOV languages have a different arrangement [4, p. 2.1]. This structural organization can affect not only grammar but also meaning and emphasis within sentences, illustrating how diverse linguistic approaches can shape communication.

Varying word orders can significantly impact clarity and emphasis in communication. For instance, in an SVO language like English, placing the object at the end can highlight it as important information. Conversely, in an SOV language, the subject is often placed first, which may prioritize the action. These differences mean that speakers must be aware of their language's syntax to effectively convey intended meanings and avoid ambiguity.

The structural features of Uzbek and English languages are so different because of their typological systems. Structural features are that grammar, word order, morphology and syntax. English, as an analytic language [2, p. 123], it uses word order and auxiliary words to express grammatical meaning. On the other hand, Uzbek is an agglutinative language that uses suffixes and case endings [6, p. 112].

WORD ORDER: English has a relatively fixed word order. The basic structure is Subject + Verb + Object. For example: She writes a letter.

Changing the word order often changes the meaning or makes the sentence ungrammatical. English uses prepositions, auxiliary verbs, and word position to show grammatical changes. For example, "The student reads the book" and "The book reads the student" have completely different meanings. This shows that English grammar depends mainly on the position of words.

Uzbek, as an agglutinative language, has a more flexible word order. Because Uzbek uses case endings (like -ni, -ga, -da), speakers can change the word order without changing the main meaning. The typical pattern is Subject + Object + Verb [1, p. 57]. For example: U xat yozadi (She writes a letter). However, for emphasis or stylistic reasons, word order can change: Xatni u yozadi (It is she who writes the letter). Grammatical relations in Uzbek are often shown through case endings, not only by position.

The three primary word order types are SVO, SOV, and VSO, however there are also variations and less common orders like VOS and OVS.

TYPOLICAL COMPARISON

Feature	English	Uzbek
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Basic pattern	SVO	SOV
Grammatical markers	Word order, prepositions	Case endings, post positions
Word order flexibility	Rigid	Flexible
Modifier position	Before noun	Before noun or after, depend on focus

The table shows the basic syntactic differences between English and Uzbek word order systems. The difference in typological structure shows how English relies more on syntactic order, while Uzbek depends on morphological markers [6, p. 210]. These differences reflect the analytic way of English and the agglutinative way of Uzbek.

The study of word order typology explains that there are different structural and typological systems of English and Uzbek languages. English follows a fixed Subject–Verb–Object (SVO) pattern, while Uzbek usually follows a Subject–Object–Verb (SOV) pattern with greater flexibility [6, p. 156]. These differences result from the analytic way of English and the agglutinative way of Uzbek. Understanding a big range of typological features helps linguists and language learners better analyze sentence structures, improve translation accuracy, and deep and easy understanding.

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TILSHUNOSLIKDA UMUMIY TAHLIL TUSHUNCHASI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisdagi lingvistikada tahlil qanday bo‘lishi va bu orqali komponent tahlil haqida bilib olish yoki tushunish uchun tasavvur paydo bo‘ladi. Komponent tahlil tushunchasi haqida o‘zbek tilshunosligidagi tadqiqotlar ot leksemalari bo‘yicha oz bo‘lganligi mavzuni o‘rganish qamrovini kengaytiradi. Maqolada tahlil uchun zarur bo‘limlar, qonun-qoidalar jamlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tahlil, morfologik, grammatik, sifatli, komponent, obyektiv tahlillar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается, каким образом проводится анализ в лингвистике и как через это можно получить представление или понимание компонентного анализа. Исследование понятия компонентного анализа в узбекском

языкознании на материале именных лексем является ограниченным, что расширяет область изучения данной темы. В статье собраны необходимые разделы, правила и принципы, применяемые при анализе.

Ключевые слова: анализ, морфологический, грамматический, качественный, компонент, объективные анализы.

Abstract: This paper discusses how analysis is conducted in linguistics and how it helps to form an understanding of component analysis. Research on the concept of component analysis in Uzbek linguistics, particularly based on noun lexemes, is limited, which broadens the scope of this study. The article compiles the essential sections, rules, and principles required for linguistic analysis.

Keywords: analysis, morphological, grammatical, qualitative, component, objective analyses.

Tildagi mavjud har qanday funksional uslub tomonidan ifoda etilayotgan xabar kabi badiiy asar matni ham nutq aktining birin-ketin keluvchi tanlangan majmuasi deb qarash mumkin. Bu esa o'z navbatida bir qator obyektiv va subyektiv, shaxsga nisbatan aloqador bo'lgan faktorlar bilan izohlanadi. Tilga olib o'tilgan faktorlarning ta'siri ko'proq ikki xil nutqda namoyon bo'ladi. Bu ikki xil nutqning birinchisi, situatsiya bilan, norasmiyligi bilan xarakterlanadi.

Tahlil yunon tilidan – ajralish, parchalanish – predmetni hodisa, jarayonni, predmetning xususiyatlarini yoki predmetlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni qismlarga: belgilar, xususiyatlar, munosabatlar tarkibiy qismlarga yoki amaliy ravishda ajratish tartibiga ajratishga asosiy e'tibor qaratilsa, [1, b-23] tarjima lug'atlarida 1 tahlil ilmiy tekshirish (tadqiqot) usuli; obyektiv voqelikni ilmiy bilish, o'rganish vositasi; 2 analiz, tahlil; tahlil qilish; kolxozning xo'jalik faoliyatini tahlil qilish; – badiiy asar tahlili; badiiy asarni tahlil qilish; 3 tahlil, tekshirish (moddalarning tarkibiy qismlarini aniqlash); – sifatli tahlil; – miqdoriy tahlil; – spektral tahlil; – qon tahlili; qonni (qon tarkibini) tahlil qilish, tekshirish; – matematik tahlil (oliy matematikaning bir bo'limi) [2, c-31] deb ilmiy tadqiqot usuli, biror jarayonni tekshirish, moddalarning tarkibini aniqlash ma'nolariga urg'u beriladi.

Morfologik tahlil. To'g'ridan-to'g'ri komponentlar bo'yicha tahlil qilish. So'zni tashkil etuvchi allofonlar va allomorflarni ma'lum bir tadqiqot darajasi uchun o'rnatilgan strukturaviy qatorlar bilan (ya'ni, tegishli fonema va morfemalar bilan) o'zaro bog'lash. Grammatik tahlil. So'zlar orasidagi grammatik bog'lanishlarni aniqlash (mos ravishda leksiklashgan iboralar). Tahlil ikkilik tahlil. Lingvistik tahlil asta-sekin ochiladigan juft qarama-qarshiliklar qatoriga asoslanadi.

Kategoriya tahlili fe'ldagi zamon quyidagi juft qarama-qarshiliklar tizimiga keltirilishi mumkin;

a) nutq lahzasini o'z ichiga oluvchi ish-harakatning belgilanishi nutq momentini o'z ichiga olmagan ish-harakatga qarama-qarshi qo'yiladi;

b) nutq momentini o'z ichiga olmagan harakatga bo'linadi; nutq momentidan oldin sodir bo'lgan va nutq paytidan keyin sodir bo'ladigan harakat va hokazo.

Sifatli tahlilda tilni tavsiflash usuli – analitik tizimga asoslangan mavjudlik – berilgan hodisaning chastotasi xususiyatlariga havola qilinmagan holda uning yo'qligi asoslangan.

Komponent tahlili cheklovchi komponentlarni aniqlash komponentlar bir xil darajadagi turli til birliklarini bir-biridan ajrata oladigan differensial xususiyatlar sifatida til birligi; chorshanba segmentatsiya. Tilning minimal mazmunli elementlarini (morflarini) aniqlash va ularning axloqiy morfemalarini aniqlashga qaratilgan lingvistik tadqiqot usullaridan biri.

Nutqiy tahlili yozma matnlarni prosodik talqin qilishning obyektiv usullarini ishlab chiqish va ayrim mualliflar tomonidan afzal ko'rgan ritmik va melodik naqshlarni aniqlashdir. Sintaktik tahlil ta'lim yoki ilmiy maqsadlarda amalga oshiriladigan gapni uning a'zolariga ajratish, gap turini aniqlash, murakkab gapni tarkibiy qismlarga ajratish va hokazo. Subyektiv tahlil qilish. Til foydalanuvchilari tomonidan ongsiz ravishda amalga oshiriladigan va ko'pincha noto'g'ri etimologiyaga, qayta parchalanishga va hokazolarga olib keladigan morfologik tahlil (so'zning parchalanishi); qarama-qarshi obyektiv tahlil. Ingliz tilidagi matnni tahlil qilish matnlarni stilistik tahlil qilish va talqin qilish, matnlarni tushuntirish. Xorijiy til darslarida matnlarni stilistik tahlil qilish va izohlash uslubiy texnika sifatida qabul qilingan.

Transformatsion tahlil. Har xil turdagi sintaktik birliklarni o'zgartirish qoidalarini ishlab chiqish va ularni elementar, "yadroli gaplar"ga qisqartirishdan iborat sintaktik tahlil turi. Tillarning miqdoriy tahlili. Til tadqiqotining statistik usuli. Yaxlit tahlil usuli. Integral usul bilan bir xil. Grammatik munosabatlarni ifodalashning perifrastik (tasviriy) usuli bilan tavsiflangan analitik tillarning morfologik tuzilishi; qarama-qarshi sintez (ikki qiymatda)dan o'tkazish va tahlil qilish uchun sintez [3, b-352].

Lingvistik tahlil o'zbek tilshunosligining nazariy bo'limlarini sistemali o'rganishning maqbul usullaridan biridir. Tahlil jarayonida til faktlari haqidagi nazariy ma'lumotlar, grammatikaning qonun-qoidalari konkret misollarda amaliyotga tatbiq qilinadi. Tahlil etuvchi har bir til faktining nazariy asoslarini puxta egallashga intiladi, Til hodisalari lingvistik tahlil asosida amaliy o'rganiladi. Lingvistik tahlil - olingan nazariy bilimlar asosida til haqidagi har bir fanning talabiga ko'ra aniq bir til yoki nutq birligini (so'z yoki gapni) parchalab o'rganishdir. Bu hodisa til o'rganuvchilarning til hodisalarini tez va to'g'ri ajrata olish malakalarini egallashlarida nazariy bilimlar bilan bir qatorda lingvistik tahlil ham muhim rol o'ynaydi [4, b-241].

Lingvistik nazariya, til sistemasi va tarixiy faktlarga asoslangan filologik tahlil. Adabiy metod, janr, badiiy-estetik prinsiplar avtor shaxsi va uning nutqiy maneriyasi va boshqa matn til ifoda vositalarining tarkibi hamda ko'rinishini belgilovchi omillardir. Lingvistik tahlil - til, nutq birliklarini uni tashkil etuvchi qismlari, mazmuni vazifasi va boshqa xususiyatlari nuqtai nazaridan tadqiq etish, til (nutq) birliklarining aniq holatini belgilash. Masalan, **hosildorlikni** so'zida ikki asil til hodisasi mavjud bo'lib, u xuddi shu hodisalar nuqtai nazaridan tahlil etilishi mumkin: 1) so'z yasalishi hodisasi; 2) shakl yasalish hodisasi (morfologik hodisa). Bu so'zda ikkita yasama so'z mavjud bo'lib, so'z yasalishi tahlilida har bir yasama so'zning tarkibi va bu tarkibiy qismlarning mohiyati vazifasi, ma'nosi va shakli belgilanadi. Bunda hosildor yasama so'z ekani, u so'z yasalish asosi hosil va so'z yasovchi -dor qo'shimchasidan iborat tarkibiy qiymatga egaligi, so'z yasalish asosi (hosil) ot turkumiga oidligi, -dor qo'shimchasining qaysi turkumga oid so'zdan qaysi turkumga mansub so'z va qanday ma'noli so'z yasashi hamda uning boshqa xususiyatlari qayd etiladi. Hosildorlik yasama so'zining tahlili ham xuddi shu tarzda olib boriladi, ya'ni u yasama so'z ekani, unda hosildor so'z yasalish asosi, -lik so'z yasovchi qo'shimcha ekani, shuningdek, bu qo'shimchaning ma'nosi va boshqa xususiyatlari qayd etiladi. Morfologik tahlilda hosildorlik so'zining ot ekanligi, -ni qo'shimchasi shu so'z (ot)ning tushum kelishik shaklini yasalishi, uning ma'nosi va shaklini qayd etiladi [5, b-59].

Xulosa qilib aytganda yer yuzidagi barcha tillar morfologik nuqtai nazardan tadqiq etilib, ularning manbalari va boshqa tillar bilan munosabatlari, yaqinligi xususida to'xtalib o'tiladi. O'zbek tilining morfologiyasiga kelsak, u agglutinativ til, ya'ni so'z oxiriga qo'shimcha qo'shish yo'li bilan so'z va shakl yasaluvchi til bo'lgani uchun so'z yasalishi hamda uning

o‘zgarishida o‘zak, negiz, qo‘shimcha, ularning birlashishi boshqa tillarga ko‘ra ancha farqli va o‘ziga xosdir.

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LANGUAGE LEARNING PSYCHOLOGY AND COGNITIVE PROCESSES

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Abstract: This paper examines the role of sociolinguistics and cultural background in the process of language acquisition. It demonstrates how societal elements, cultural expectations, and personal identity shape the way learners’ approach and apply a new language. The research underlines the necessity of combining cultural sensitivity with linguistic skills to achieve meaningful interaction. It also addresses the difficulties learners encounter when cultural insight is insufficient. The primary goal of this study is to prove that mastering a language requires more than grammar and vocabulary; it demands an understanding of the traditions and social values connected to it.

Keywords: language learning, psychology, cognition, motivation, memory, vocabulary, study.

Language learning is a multifaceted process that engages cognitive, psychological, and social dimensions. It extends beyond the simple memorization of words and rules to include the learner’s ability to perceive, process, and apply language in meaningful contexts. Emotional readiness, personal motivation, and social interaction are central to successful acquisition. Learners who are confident, curious, and culturally aware are more likely to practice actively and retain knowledge effectively.

In contemporary globalized societies, linguistic competence alone is insufficient. A grammatically correct sentence may still fail to convey meaning appropriately if it does not align with cultural norms. Understanding gestures, idioms, humor, and etiquette within a specific culture is therefore essential. Language learning becomes a process of cognitive engagement combined with social adaptation, where learners must navigate both mental and cultural frameworks simultaneously.

Scholars have long examined the intersection of psychology, cognition, and language acquisition. Vygotsky’s sociocultural theory emphasizes the importance of interaction,

claiming that knowledge is constructed through communication and collaborative activities. This approach underlines the role of cultural context, suggesting that language cannot be effectively learned in isolation from social experience.

Chomsky's Universal Grammar theory highlights innate cognitive mechanisms that enable humans to acquire language naturally. While it explains the mental architecture for syntax and sentence formation, researchers argue that real-world language use also depends on environmental and social factors. Krashen's Input Hypothesis further indicates that learners require comprehensible input within a low-stress environment, as affective filters—such as anxiety or fear of errors—can impede progress.

Contemporary research by Norton and Byram emphasizes the role of identity, intercultural competence, and social participation. Language learners who engage with cultural content and authentic communication opportunities develop greater confidence and pragmatic skills. Cognitive psychologists also stress memory, attention, and executive function as key determinants of effective learning, recommending strategies like spaced repetition, visualization, and contextualized practice. Motivation is a central determinant in language acquisition. Learners driven by intrinsic motivation—curiosity, interest, or personal goals—demonstrate more consistent practice and resilience compared to those motivated solely by grades or external rewards. Anxiety, self-confidence, and emotional state can either enhance or inhibit learning. For instance, learners who fear mistakes may avoid speaking, limiting their exposure and fluency. Memory, perception, and problem-solving are essential for acquiring vocabulary and mastering grammar. Learners form associations between new concepts and existing knowledge, which strengthens retention. Techniques such as repetition, mnemonic devices, and context-based learning enhance cognitive processing and long-term recall. Neurocognitive studies also suggest that regular exposure and active use of language can rewire neural pathways, improving linguistic performance across age groups.

Cultural competence is crucial for pragmatic and effective communication. A student may construct grammatically correct sentences yet fail to express politeness, irony, or formality correctly. Exposure to authentic cultural materials, interaction with native speakers, and participation in group discussions help learners internalize sociocultural norms. Social dynamics, such as age, gender, and social status, further influence language use and comprehension. This research employs a qualitative descriptive approach, synthesizing findings from psycholinguistic, cognitive, and sociolinguistic studies. Comparative analysis of theoretical frameworks and observational data from classroom practices was conducted to examine how psychological, cognitive, and cultural factors influence language learning. Case studies and practical examples illustrate the integration of cognitive strategies with cultural understanding, highlighting effective teaching and learning methods. Language learning is a holistic process encompassing cognitive skills, emotional readiness, and cultural understanding.

True proficiency is achieved when learners combine memory, problem-solving, motivation, and social adaptation with an awareness of cultural norms. Educators should design curricula that integrate interactive exercises, cultural content, and cognitive strategy training. By emphasizing the interplay between psychology, cognition, and social context, language instruction becomes more meaningful, effective, and aligned with real-life communication needs.

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INTERFERENSIYA VA UNING TURLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada lingvistik interferensiya hodisasining mohiyati, u haqida olimlarning ayrim qarashlari va uning kelib chiqish sabablari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada interferensiya til o‘rganish jarayonining tabiiy natijasi sifatida talqin qilingan va uning turlari misollar orqali yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: interferensiya, sotsiolingvistika, areal lingvistika, fonetik, leksik, sintaktik, grammatik interferensiya, til va dialektlar ittifoqi.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется сущность лингвистического явления интерференции, рассматриваются отдельные взгляды учёных по данной проблеме и причины её возникновения. Интерференция интерпретируется как естественный результат процесса изучения языка, а её виды раскрываются на конкретных примерах.

Ключевые слова: интерференция, социолингвистика, ареальная лингвистика, фонетическая, лексическая, синтаксическая, грамматическая интерференция, союз языков и диалектов.

Abstract: This article analyzes the essence of the linguistic phenomenon of interference, presents several scholars' views on the subject, and examines the causes of its occurrence. The study interprets interference as a natural result of the language learning process and illustrates its types through specific examples.

Keywords: interference, sociolinguistics, areal linguistics, phonetic, lexical, syntactic, grammatical interference, language and dialect union.

Kirish: Bugungi kunda bir necha tillarni bilish va u tillarda bermalol muloqot qila olish hayotimizning birlamchi ehtiyojiga aylanib bormoqda. Shu tufayli dunyoda bilingvlar va polingvlarning tobora ko‘payib borayotgani tabiiy holdir. Har bir bilingv nutqida ikkinchi tilni o‘zlashtirish va uni qo‘llash jarayoni tufayli ona tiliga bo‘lgan ta‘sirini yoki ona tilining o‘rganayotgan tilga bo‘lgan ta‘sirini bevosita kuzatamiz. Bu albatta, bilingvning so‘zlashuv jarayonida turli fonetik, leksik, grammatik muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu jarayonda biz interferensiya hodisasiga murojaat qilamiz.

Muhokama: Interferensiya lotincha so‘zdan olingan bo‘lib inter – o‘zaro va ferens – ko‘tarish, urilish degan ma‘nolarni anglatadi. Interferensiya terminiga fizikada “to‘lqinlarning fazoda ustma-ust tushib qo‘shilgan holda bir-birini kuchaytirishi yoki susaytirishi”, biologiyada “gomologik xromosomalar bir uchastkasidagi krossingoverning boshqa qo‘shni uchastkalarda yangi krossingover paydo bo‘lishiga ta‘siri”, tibbiyotda “aralash (bir necha xil virus tufayli kelib chiqqan) infeksiyada bir virusning boshqa virus ta‘sirini bosib ketishi” deya ta‘rif beriladi [1]. Tilshunoslikda bu hodisa qanday izohlanadi? Turli adabiyotlarda turlicha ta‘riflarni kuzatishimiz mumkin:

Interferensiya – ona tiliga xos xususiyatlarni o‘rganilayotgan tilga o‘tkazish. (Bu til odatda qarindosh til bo‘lmaydi) [2]. Interferensiya – so‘zlovchi birinchi tilining keyinchalik o‘rganadigan tiliga maqsadli ta‘siri. Masalan, fransuzlarning ingliz tilidagi ‘th’ tovushini [s] tarzida talaffuz qilishi [3].

Interferensiya keng ma‘noda ikki tilli shaxslar nutqida yuzaga keladigan har ikki tilning me‘yorlardan chetga chiqishi, tor ma‘noda ikki tilli shaxsning yozma va og‘zaki nutqida ona tili ta‘sirida ikkinchi til me‘yorlaridan chetga chiqishi [4].

Ushbu ta‘riflardan kelib chiqib, interferensiya – polinngvlar nutqida yuz beruvchi ikki yoki undan ortiq tillarning o‘zaro ta‘siri natijasida til birliklarining noto‘g‘ri qo‘llanishi deya izohlashimiz mumkin.

Uriel Weinreich o‘zining “Languages in contact” (O‘zaro aloqadagi tillar) asarida nutqdagi va tildagi interferensiyani farqlaydi: “Nutqda interferensiya oqim tomonidan olib ketilgan qumga o‘xshaydi; tilda bu ko‘l tubidagi cho‘kindi qumdir. Nutqda u ikki tilli so‘zlovchining boshqa tilni shaxsiy o‘rganishi, bilishi natijasida so‘zlashuvlarida yangidan paydo bo‘ladi. Tilda biz ikki tillilarning nutqida tez-tez uchraydigan, odatlanib qolgan va o‘rnatilgan interferensiyani uchratamiz. Agar X tilda so‘zlashuvchi Y tilidan ma‘lum bir shaklni tabiiy holda o‘zlashtirib olmay, balki uni boshqa X tilida so‘zlashuvchilar tomonidan qo‘llaganini eshitganligi uchun ishlatsa, bu o‘zlashtirilgan elementni tavsiflovchi nuqtayi nazardan X tilining bir qismiga aylangan deb hisoblashimiz mumkin”[5]. Masalan, bugungi kunda rus tilini to‘liq o‘zlashtirmagan o‘zbeklar nutqida ham *уже, зато, обидно* kabi rus tilidagi so‘zlarning ishlatilishi odat tusiga aylangan.

Natijalar: Interferensiya tilning turli sathlarida namoyon bo‘lishi mumkin. Shu jihatdan uni bir necha turlarga ajratamiz:

- a) fonetik interferensiya;
- b) grammatik interferensiya;
- d) leksik interferensiya;
- e) sintaktik interferensiya.

Fonetik interferensiya ikki tilli shaxslar tilida eng keng tarqalgan va ko‘p uchraydigan nutqiy hodisadir. Bunda ikki tilning o‘zaro ta‘siri tufayli so‘zlovchi talaffuzidagi buzilishlar nazarda tutiladi. Masalan, o‘zbeklarning ingliz tilidagi ‘this’ so‘zini (zis) tarzida talaffuz qilishi. Fonetik interferensiya nutq tovushlarining talaffuzi, urg‘u, intonatsiya, ritm jarayonida yuzaga chiqadi. Bunda so‘zlovchi ikkinchi tilda so‘zlayotganda ona tiliga xos ohangni, urg‘uni, tovushlarni qo‘llaydi va aksent yuzaga keladi. Masalan, o‘zbek tilida so‘z urg‘usi odatda oxirgi bo‘g‘inga tushgani tufayli rus tilidagi so‘zlarni ham shu tarzda talaffuz qilish aksentni keltirib chiqaradi.

Grammatik interferensiya tildagi grammatik shakllarni noto‘g‘ri qo‘llash tufayli kelib chiqadi. Dastlab ko‘pgina tilshunos olimlar tillarning bir-biriga grammatik, morfologik ta‘sir qila olish imkoniyatiga shubha ostida qaraydilar. “Ikki tilning grammatik tizimi bir biriga o‘ta olmaydi” – deya ta‘kidlaydi Meillet o‘zining “Tarixiy tilshunoslik va umumiy tilshunoslik” asarida va uning fikriga qo‘shilgan holda Sapir ham takrorlaydi: “Biz hech qayerda ba‘zi yuzaki morfologik ta‘sirlardan boshqasini uchratmaymiz”. Schuchardt esa bu fikrga qarshi chiqadi. Lekin Weinreich bu tortishuvlarning sababi ular o‘rtasida asosiy atamalar va tushunchalar bo‘yicha kelishuv yo‘qligida deb biladi va grammatik interferensiya mavjudligini isbotlaydi [6].

Leksik interferensiya bu ikki (yoki undan ortiq) tilda so‘zlashuvchi kishilar nutqida leksik birliklarning noto‘g‘ri qo‘llanilishidir. Leksik interferensiya nutqimizning umuman boshqa ma‘noga aylanib ketishi va hamsuhbatimizning noto‘g‘ri tushunishiga olib kelishi

mumkin. Bu xatolar soʻzlarni bir tildan ikkinchi tilga toʻgʻridan toʻgʻri tarjima qilish, soʻzni notoʻgʻri tanlash sababli kelib chiqadi.

Sintaktik interferensiya bu bir tilning sintaktik qoidalari boshqa tilga nooʻrin tarzda koʻchirilishi natijasida yuzaga keladigan xatolikdir.

XULOSA: Xulosa qilib aytganda, interferensiya tabiiy ravishda yuzaga keluvchi hodisa boʻlib, ikki yoki undan ortiq tillarning oʻzaro taʼsiri natijasida kelib chiqadi. Bugungi kunda til oʻrganish jarayonidagi kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish va nutq madaniyatini oshirishga qaratilgan ishlar dolzarbdir. Shunday ekan, interferensiyani chuqur tahlil qilib, uning turlari, sabablari va bartaraf etish yoʻllarini aniqlash muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MORPHOLOGICAL SYSTEMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: This article presents a comparative analysis of the morphological systems of English and Uzbek. The grammatical structures, morphological types, word formation methods, verb systems, case and possessive categories, as well as the affixation systems of both languages, are examined in depth. The study reveals that English is classified as an analytical language, while Uzbek belongs to the agglutinative language type. Additionally, the article highlights the role of morphological differences in language learning, translation processes, and language teaching practices.

Keywords: morphology, analytical language, agglutinative language, grammatical category, affix, word formation, verb form, case, possession.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarining morfologik tizimlari qiyosiy jihatdan o'rganiladi. Har ikki tilning grammatik tuzilishi, morfologik tipi, so'z yasash usullari, fe'l tizimi, kelishik va egalik kategoriyalari, shuningdek, qo'shimchalar tizimi chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijasida ingliz tili analitik, o'zbek tili esa agglutinativ til tipiga mansub ekani aniqlanadi. Shuningdek, maqolada morfologik farqlarning til o'rganish, tarjima jarayoni va lingvodidaktik amaliyotdagi o'rni ham yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: morfologiya, analitik til, agglutinativ til, grammatik kategoriya, qo'shimcha, so'z yasalishi, fe'l shakli, kelishik, egalik.

Аннотация: В данной статье сравнительно исследуются морфологические системы английского и узбекского языков. Глубоко проанализированы грамматическая структура обоих языков, морфологический тип, способы словообразования, система глаголов, категории спряжения и владения, а также система суффиксов. В результате исследования установлено, что английский язык относится к аналитическому, а узбекский - к агглютинативному языковому типу. В статье также рассматривается роль морфологических различий в изучении языка, процессе перевода и лингводидактической практике.

Ключевые слова: морфология, аналитический язык, агглютинативный язык, грамматическая категория, дополнение, словообразование, глагольная форма, спряжение, притяжение.

In every language, the morphological system plays a central role in the grammatical structure. Morphology studies the form and structure of words, as well as their grammatical meanings. The morphological systems of different languages are influenced by their historical development, typological features, and syntactic structures.

English and Uzbek belong to two different morphological types. English is an analytical language, meaning that grammatical meanings are primarily expressed through auxiliary words, word order, and functional units. Uzbek, on the other hand, is an agglutinative language, where grammatical meanings are mainly conveyed through affixes added to the root word [1, 150 p.].

As a result, word forms in English change very little, whereas in Uzbek, a single word can take on multiple grammatical meanings through the addition of various affixes. These differences are highly significant in linguistics, translation, and foreign language teaching.

Therefore, this article provides a systematic analysis of the morphological structures of both languages.

1. *Morphological Type and Grammatical Structure.* English has an analytical structure, meaning that grammatical meanings are expressed not through affixes, but through auxiliary words, prepositions, and word order. For example: *I am reading a book* - in this sentence, the auxiliary verb “*am*” indicates the present continuous tense.

Uzbek, on the other hand, is an agglutinative language, where grammatical meanings are expressed through a system of affixes. For example, in the word *o‘qimoqdaman* (“I am reading”), the affixes *-moq*, *-da*, and *-man* indicate the verbal noun, tense, and person-number respectively.

Therefore, in English, *syntax* (word order) plays the primary role, while in Uzbek, *morphology* (the affixation system) takes the leading position.

2. *Word Formation and Affixation System.* In English, word formation is carried out through the use of prefixes and suffixes. *Prefixes* are added to the beginning of a word to change its meaning (*unhappy*, *rewrite*, *dislike*). *Suffixes* change the grammatical category or part of speech (*teacher*, *happiness*, *national*). In Uzbek, however, only *suffixal word formation* exists (*do‘st – do‘stlik*, *yaxshi – yaxshilik*, *o‘qit – o‘qituvchi*), and there are no prefixes. In this respect, Uzbek has a rich system of affixes, and new words are mainly formed through suffixation [2, 57 p.]. In contrast, in English, new words are often formed through *compounding* (the combination of two or more words), as in *blackboard* or *greenhouse*.

3. *Verb System and Tense Category.* Verb morphology in both languages is complex, but the means of expressing grammatical meanings differ significantly.

In English, there are **12 main tenses**, formed using *auxiliary verbs* such as *be*, *have*, *do*, and *will* [3.300 p]. For example: *I have eaten*. *I will be reading*

In Uzbek, there are **three main tenses**: present, past, and future (*boraman – I will go*, *bordim – I went*, *borayapman – I am going*). Additionally, Uzbek uses *mood affixes* (for desire, condition, command) and *person-number suffixes*, whereas English conveys these meanings using *auxiliary words or modal verbs* (*can*, *must*, *should*).

Example: *Men boraman* – person and tense are expressed in a single verb form.

I will go – person (*I*) and tense (*will*) are expressed as separate words.

4. *Case and Possessive Systems.* In English, the *case system* is almost nonexistent [4.]; grammatical relationships are expressed using *prepositions*, such as *to the school*, *from the city*, *in the house*.

In Uzbek, however, there are **six grammatical cases**:

1. *Bosh kelishik (Nominative) (base form): Ali o‘qiyapti (Ali studies)*
2. *Qaratqich kelishigi (Genitive)(-ning) : Alining kitobi (Ali’s book).*
3. *Tushum kelishigi (Accusative) (-ni): Kitobni oldim (I took the book)*
4. *Jo‘nalish kelishigi (Dative)(-ga): Maktabga bordim (I went to school)*
5. *O‘rin -payt kelishigi (Locative) (-da): Uyda o‘qiyman (I study at home)*
6. *Chiqish kelishigi (Ablative) (-dan): Uydan ketaman (I go from home)*

The *possessive category* is also expressed differently in the two languages.

In English, possession is indicated by *'s* or the preposition *of* (*Ali’s book*, *the book of Ali*). In Uzbek, it is expressed through *possessive suffixes* (*kitobim – my book*, *kitobing – your book*, *kitobi – his/her book*).

5. *Word Order and Syntactic Relations.* In English, **word order is strict** [5], typically following the **S + V + O** (Subject + Verb + Object) pattern: *She reads books*.

In Uzbek, however, **word order is flexible** [6, 247 p.]:

U kitob o‘qiydi

Kitobni u o'qiydi
O'qiydi u kitobni

All of these are grammatically correct, but each emphasizes a different part of the sentence. This distinction is important in both translation and language teaching: In English, word order determines grammatical meaning. In Uzbek, it conveys emphasis or focus in meaning.

6. *Morphological Simplicity and Semantic Richness*. English morphology is relatively **simple**, but **semantically complex**. A single word can express different meanings depending on the context.

For example, in English *run* can mean to move quickly; to operate a machine; to manage a company. In contrast, Uzbek morphology is **complex**, but meanings are **clearly and explicitly marked** through affixes [7.245 p.].

For instance:

boraman (I will go),

bormadim (I did not go),

bormasam (if I don't go),

bormasdim (I wouldn't have gone), etc.

Thus, Uzbek stands out for the richness of its word forms, while English is notable for its syntactic flexibility.

The results of the study show that the morphological systems of English and Uzbek differ fundamentally. English is morphologically simple but syntactically rigid, while Uzbek is morphologically rich but syntactically flexible. These differences significantly affect the mechanisms by which grammatical meanings are conveyed in each language. Therefore, a deep understanding of these differences is crucial in the process of **foreign language learning and translation**.

In conclusion, the differences between the morphological systems of English and Uzbek languages reflect not only grammatical, but also cultural and contemplative aspects. English, as an analytical language, can express complex meanings through simple forms, while Uzbek, representing a system of suffixes, embodies several grammatical meanings of the same word.

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TILSHUNOSLIKDA DOLZARB YO'NALISHLAR VA MUAMMOLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada tilshunoslikning ayni davrdagi dolzarb hisoblanadigan yo'nalishlari hamda ularning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari yoritilib o'tiladi. Xususan, kognitiv lingvistika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, kompyuter lingvistikasi, tarjimashunoslik nazariyasi kabi sohalarda olib borilayotgan izlanishlar tahlil qilinadi va tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari, sun'iy ong va global muloqot sharoitida tilning o'rni, uning saqlab qolinishi va rivojlanib borishi singari muammolar o'z aksini topadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, kognitiv lingvistika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, kompyuter lingvistikasi, tarjimashunoslik, metodologik muammolar, global muloqot, axborot texnologiyalari, sun'iy ong, til rivoji.

Abstract: This article discusses the current trends in linguistics and their scientific and theoretical foundations. In particular, research in such areas as cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, computational linguistics, and translation theory is analyzed and explained. It also reflects on the role of language in the context of modern information technologies, artificial intelligence, and global communication, as well as problems such as its preservation and development.

Keywords: linguistics, cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, computational linguistics, translation studies, methodological problems, global communication, information technologies, artificial intelligence, language development.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные тенденции в лингвистике и их научно-теоретические основы. В частности, анализируются и освещаются исследования в таких областях, как когнитивная лингвистика, социолингвистика, психолингвистика, компьютерная лингвистика и теория перевода. Также рассматривается роль языка в контексте современных информационных технологий, искусственного интеллекта и глобальной коммуникации, а также проблемы его сохранения и развития.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, когнитивная лингвистика, социолингвистика, психолингвистика, компьютерная лингвистика, переводоведение, методологические проблемы, глобальная коммуникация, информационные технологии, искусственный интеллект, развитие языка.

Tilshunoslikning nazariyasini yangi bosqichga olib chiqarish uchun mashhur olimlarning ilmiy ishlari yuksak ahamiyat kasb etadi. Misol qilib oladigan bo'lsak, N. Chomsky tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan generativ grammatika nazariyasi tilning universalligi va inson ongida mavjud bo'lgan "tilni tabiiy o'rganish qobiliyati" yondashuvini izohlab berdi. Bu nazariya hozirgi kognitiv lingvistikaning shakllanishida poydevor ilmiy nazariyadir. U. Labovning sotsiolingvistika bo'yicha tadqiqotlari esa tilni ijtimoiy jihatdan tabaqalinishi, ijtimoiy guruhlar va muloqot sharoitidagi xilma-xillik bilan tahlil qilish imkonini berdi.

Hozirgi kunda tilshunoslik sohasida xalqaro, shuningdek, mahalliy olimlarning izlanishlari ham alohida e'tiborga sazovor sanaladi. Avvalo, Deborah Tannenning gender va muloqot bo'yicha tadqiqotlari til va ijtimoiy munosabatlarning murakkab munosabatlarini ko'rsatib beradi. O'zbek tilshunosligida esa Sh. Safarov kognitiv lingvistikada ilmiy ishlar yo'lga qo'yib, til va tafakkur masalalariga oid qarashlarni aytib o'tdi [3]. A. Madvaliyev, N.

Mahmudov va boshqa olimlarning tadqiqotlari esa o'zbek tili grammatikasi, leksikologiyasi va uslubiyatida yangi yondashuvlari ilmiy sohada munosib o'rin egalladi.

1. *Kognitiv lingvistika va tilning tafakkur bilan uzviy bog'liqligi*. "Bola hech qachon eshitmagan jummalarni ham tuzib, tushunib bera oladi. Bu esa inson ongida tug'ma generativ qobiliyat mavjudligidan dalolat beradi"[1,p.18]. Uning bu nazariyasidan kelib chiqadiki, N. Chomsky til o'rganish va o'zlashtirish qobiliyatini inson ongida tug'ma ravishda mavjud bo'lgan universal mexanizm asosiy vazifa bajaradi [2]. Kognitiv lingvistika vakillari – J. Lakoff va M. Jonson esa "Metaphors We Live By" (1980) asarida metafora (qiyoslash)ni inson tafakkurining asosiy ishlash prinsipi sifatida aytib o'tishdi. Nazariyasining ma'nosiga ko'ra, inson tafakkuri mavhum tushunchalarni ko'p hollarda aniq amaliy tajribalar orqali anglaydi. Masalan, vaqtni fazo orqali tasavvur qilish (kelgusidagi ertaga va o'tmishdagi kecha) shular jumlasidandir. Insonning dunyoqarashini shakllantiruvchi asosiy omillardan biri til va uni o'rganish sanaladi, til shunchaki ijtimoiy vosita emas.

O'zbek tilshunosligida ham alohida rivojlanayotgan soha – kognitiv tilshunoslik. Sh. Safarovning ilmiy izlanishlari til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi aloqani ijtimoiy va milliy tafakkur xususiyatlari bilan bog'lab o'rganishda muhim qadam bo'ldi. Masalan, o'zbek tilida ishlatiladigan "ko'ngil" tushunchasi nafaqat inson organiga, balki ruhiy holat, ichki kechinma va ma'naviy dunyoni ham ifodalaydi. Bu esa til birliklarining semantik chegaralari va kontekstdagi mazmuni milliy tafakkur bilan bevosita bog'liq ekanini ko'rsatadi. Sh. Safarov aytganidek, "Til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganish kognitiv lingvistikaning asosiy vazifasidir." [4,p.16].

2. *Kompyuter lingvistikasi va yangi texnologiyalarning ta'siri*. XX asr o'rtalaridan boshlab kompyuter lingvistikasi va yangi texnologiyalar sohasida izlanishlar kuchaydi, sababi texnika va texnologiyalar asri boshlanish arafasida edi. 1950-yillarda A. Turing tomonidan ilgari surilgan mashhur "Turing testi" tizimi texnikalarning inson nutqini qay darajada anglay olish, tushunish qobiliyatini tekshirish mezoni sifatida ilm-fanga olib kirgan. Bugungi kunda esa sun'iy intellekt tizimlari nafaqat oddiy muloqot olib boradi, balki yangicha matn yaratadi, nutqni analiz-sintez qiladi, tezlikda tarjima ishlarini amalga oshiradi. Google Translate, ChatGPT va boshqa GPT kabi tizimlar kompyuter lingvistikasining zamonaviy dunyodagi amaliy yutuqlaridir.

Hozirgi axborot bazalarning zamonaviy ko'rinishi bo'lmish korpus "korpus lingvistikasi"ga poydevor bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda. Korpus lingvistikasi kompyuter lingvistikasi doirasida alohida ahamiyatga ega, sababi millionlab matnlardan iborat elektron bazalar bo'lib, baza til birliklari(so'zlari, so'z birikmalari, atamalar, frazalar)ning hayotda qo'llanishilini statistik tahlil qiladi.

Masalan, ingliz tilini tadqiq etish uchun qo'llanadigan bir qancha xorijiy korpuslar bo'lib, ular British National Corpus (BNC) yoki Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) deb ataladi. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham "O'zbek tilining milliy korpusi" loyihasi yo'lga qo'yilgan bo'lib, bu tilni zamonaviy elektron muhitda tadqiq qilish va o'qitishda katta imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Ilmiy fakt sifatida ta'kidlash joizki, kompyuter lingvistikasi sun'iy intellektning asosiy tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi va u kelajakda inson-mashina o'zaro aloqasini yanada mukammal darajaga olib chiqishi kutilmoqda. Masalan, nutqni real vaqtda sintez qiluvchi neyron tarmoqlar yordamida mashinalar inson nutqiga o'xshash ohang, intonatsiya va hissiy rang berishi mumkinligi allaqachon isbotlangan.

3. *Sotsiolingvistika va tilning ijtimoiy tabaqalanishi*. Sotsiolingvistika tilshunoslikning jamiyat bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lgan eng muhim yo'nalishidir. Bu fan tilni sof lingvistik tizim emas, balki ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida ko'rib, uning jamiyatdagi tabaqalanishi, guruhlararo

farqlanishi va kommunikativ vazifalarini tahlil qiladi. Til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi uzviy aloqani ilmiy jihatdan asoslab bergan olimlardan biri - U. Labov bo'lib, u "Sotsiolingvistik naqshlar" (Sociolinguistic Patterns, 1972) asarida tilning ijtimoiy qatlamlarga qarab farqlanishini isbotladi. Masalan, Nyu-Yorkdagi turli ijtimoiy guruh vakillari nutqidagi farqlar fonetik, leksik va grammatik xususiyatlarda yaqqol namoyon bo'lishini ilmiy tajribalar asosida ko'rsatdi.

Tilning ijtimoiy tabaqalanishi va darajalanishining zamirida gender masalasi ham yotadi. Deborah Tannen o'z tadqiqotlarida erkaklar va ayollarning muloqot uslublaridagi farqlarni ko'rsatib, tilning gender stereotiplari va jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy rollar bilan aloqadorligini yoritish bilan birgalikda, "Ayollar suhbatlarda yaqinlikni saqlash uchun tilni ishlatadilar, bu esa 'rapport-talk' deb ataladi.", deya ta'kidlab o'tgan.[5,p.17] D.Tannenning bu kabi ijtimoiy munosabatlar negizida tilning rivojlanishi, tildan foydalanilishi birvarakayiga sotsiologiya, psixologiya, shuningdek, lingvistika sohalariga muhim yangiliklarni olib keldi.

Ushbu ilmiy izlanishlarni ko'rib chiqqach shunita'kidlash joizki, tilshunoslik nafaqat nazariy bilimlarni boyitadi, balki jamiyat hayotida, madaniyatlararo munosabatda hamda texnologik rivojlanishda bevosita o'rin egallaydi. Tilni yaxlit o'rganib chiqish inson tafakkuri, ijtimoiy-madaniy muhit va texnologik taraqqiyotning bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'liqligini chuqurroq anglashga imkon beradi.

Tilshunoslik tadqiqotlari fanlararo sohasini kengaytirib, kognitiv(aqliy) va neyrolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika va pragmalingvistika, kompyuter lingvistikasi va tarjimashunoslikni integratsiyalashtirish natijasida rivojlantirishni ko'zda tutish darkor. Xulosa qilib aytganda, tilshunoslik fani nazariy va amaliy jihatdan yanada kengaygan holda ilmiy taraqqiyotda o'zining global o'rnini topish va mustahkamlash imkoniga ega.

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LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TERMINOLOGICAL SYNONYMY IN THE FIELD OF GEOLOGY

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Abstract: This article examines the phenomenon of terminological synonymy in the field of geology. It identifies the main types and linguistic features of synonymous terms in English and Uzbek geological terminology. Based on data from bilingual geological dictionaries, the study reveals that synonymy accounts for a notable portion of geological terminology, reflecting both linguistic diversity and scientific development. The findings emphasise the importance of synonymy in enriching professional vocabulary and enhancing precision in scientific communication.

Keywords: synonymous terms, lexical component, synonyms, lexical-semantic basis, grammatical synonymy, grammatical meaning, lexical meaning.

The lexical units chosen by an expert in the communication process form their unique features of the world's linguistic landscape. Lexico-semantic processes, widespread at the verbal level, actively influence the thesaurus level and the pragmatics of linguistic personality. Researchers believe that “the lexical-semantic system more than others ensures the functioning of language as a means of communication”, and the lexical component (lexicon, lexicon) in the communication of specialists in a particular field of knowledge is “the most accurate guide to the study of cognitive activity and to understand the modelling of everyday discourse.” Therefore, the analysis of the theoretical foundations and pragmatics of the lexical component in the linguistic worldview of a specialist is one of the main focuses of modern research in the field of terminology.

Methods and Analyses. Synonyms are one of the factors that show the richness of any language. Here, R. Doniyorov, who studied the terminology of the Uzbek language, gave the following definition to the synonyms. “Synonyms are lexemes that express a semantically close or similar concept and differ from each other by signs of meaning or stylistic colouring.” Accordingly, I. Siddiqova specifically points out the possibility of their lexical replacement in the text as a criterion for determining whether words are synonyms. Based on the above definitions, it is explained that the terms and lexemes related to geology are synonymous in the English and Uzbek languages and that they are semantically similar and close. Each gemstone, mineral or concept used in the field of geology is represented by a term, one of which has the main meaning, and others are used as synonyms, antonyms and homonyms. requires widespread use. For example: Eng. *acmite* – English terms such as *aegirine*, *aegirite*, Uzbek. *larnite* (chemical formula $Sa_2 [SiO_4]$) is a synonym for terms such as *belite* and *felite*;

In international geological terminology, we found that three prefixes are synonymous with each other due to their chemical composition, and the terms formed by them exhibit the feature of synonymy. They have the same meaning but differ in form. For example: Alumino, Alumo - Iron Fe, Auri, Auro - Gold Au, Iodine, Iodine - Iodine are prefixes. Sometimes it is appropriate to use the following terms interchangeably in the English and Uzbek languages: (*alumino*, *alumo*) *alumosungstite* - *alumosungstite* - structurally a mixture of aluminum and tungsten substances, *aluminocopiapite* - *aluminocopiapite* - structurally a mineral consisting of a mixture of copiapite and aluminum consists of substances, (Auri, Auro) Auricuprid — Auricuprid – a mineral consisting of gold and copper substances, Aurostibit — Aurostibit – a mineral consisting of a mixture of gold and antimony substances, (iodine, iodine) Iodargyrite - Iodargyrite - an ore consisting of iodine and silver, Iodobromite - Iodobromite - an ore consisting of iodine and bromine. As observed in the terminology of other fields, the phenomenon of synonymy was observed in the semantic structure of geological terms.

In particular, B.A. Isakhodjayev and others. In the “Russian-Uzbek Annotated Dictionary of Geological Terms”, which contains about 7400 terms, 301 terms have synonymous lines, and more than 900 terms are synonymous with each other, as determined by statistical analysis. This means that 12% of the total number of geological terms form a line of synonyms. Also in the bilingual dictionary “Anglo-Russian Geological Dictionary (English-Uzbek Geological Dictionary)”, which covers about 52,000 geological terms compiled by lexicographers such as P.P. Timofeyev, M.N. Alekseyev, T.A. Sofiano, English 925 was included in the analysis. Although terms have synonymous lines in the English language, more than 2,700 terms can form a mutually synonymous relationship, suggesting that 5% of all geological terms in the English language form a synonymous line. In short, it is no exaggeration to say that synonymy is one of the widespread linguistic phenomena in professional terminology, based on the information in the geological dictionaries of English

and Uzbek languages. We found it appropriate to explain these theoretical ideas, presented in Uzbek and English, using the following geological terms.

The synonyms appearing in Uzbek and English geological terminology can be characterized as follows: 1) synonyms between fields or within fields; 2) presence of quantitative differences of terms in the synonym line; 3) the structure of terms in synonymous lines; 4) reasons for the appearance of synonymous lines; 5) analyzed according to their characteristics such as absolute synonyms or relative synonyms.

The conducted analysis shows that terminological synonymy in geology is a widespread and natural linguistic process that enriches professional vocabulary. English and Uzbek geological terminologies demonstrate a high degree of synonymic variation resulting from both linguistic and scientific developments. The data from geological dictionaries confirm that 5–12% of terms have synonymous counterparts, reflecting the dynamic and evolving nature of scientific terminology. Synonymy not only enhances lexical diversity but also improves the precision and expressiveness of scientific communication in both languages.

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METAPHOR AND COGNITIVE MODELS IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article examines the role of metaphor in shaping cognitive models within modern English. Drawing on the principles of cognitive linguistics, particularly the work of Lakoff and Johnson (1980), the study explores how metaphors reflect and influence the way speakers conceptualize abstract domains such as time, emotion, and social relations. By analyzing authentic examples from contemporary discourse, media, and literature, the research demonstrates that metaphors are not merely stylistic devices but fundamental mechanisms of thought. The study concludes that understanding metaphorical conceptualization is crucial for linguistic analysis, foreign language teaching, and intercultural communication, as metaphors reveal deep cultural and cognitive patterns.

Keywords: metaphor, cognitive models, cognitive linguistics, modern English, conceptualization.

Introduction. Metaphor has traditionally been studied as a rhetorical device, employed for aesthetic or persuasive effect. However, the emergence of cognitive linguistics in the late twentieth century shifted the understanding of metaphor from ornamentation to cognition. According to Lakoff and Johnson (1980), metaphors are central to human thought, shaping how individuals conceptualize abstract phenomena. Phrases such as time is money or argument is war reveal that metaphorical mapping underpins much of everyday language use. In modern English, metaphors pervade not only literature and creative writing but also political discourse, advertising, journalism, and everyday conversation. This article explores how metaphors contribute to the construction of cognitive models in contemporary English and why their study is essential for linguistic analysis, language teaching, and intercultural communication.

Literature Review. Lakoff and Johnson's seminal work *Metaphors We Live By* (1980) introduced the idea that metaphors are not linguistic embellishments but conceptual structures. Their Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) identifies systematic mappings between source domains (concrete experiences) and target domains (abstract concepts). Kövecses (2002) expanded on this framework, emphasizing cultural variation in metaphorical patterns.

Cameron and Low (1999) highlighted the pedagogical implications of metaphor, showing that awareness of metaphorical language enhances comprehension and interpretation in foreign language learning. Charteris-Black (2004) analyzed metaphor in political discourse, illustrating its persuasive power. Recent research (Semino, 2008; Gibbs, 2017) has further demonstrated that metaphors play a role in framing public understanding of issues such as health, economy, and social relations.

These studies collectively affirm that metaphor is both a linguistic and cognitive phenomenon with profound cultural implications.

Methodology. This research adopts a qualitative approach, drawing on discourse analysis and examples from contemporary English. The sources include newspapers, online media, literary works, and conversational English. Metaphorical expressions were identified and classified according to Conceptual Metaphor Theory. The analysis focuses on three major domains: time, emotion, and social relations, as these are among the most metaphorically rich areas of English.

Results and Discussion. The findings indicate that metaphorical language structures fundamental aspects of how English speakers perceive reality. One of the most prominent domains is time, frequently conceptualized through economic metaphors. Expressions such as spending time, wasting time, and investing time reveal that time is framed as a valuable commodity. This cognitive model reflects capitalist and efficiency-driven values in contemporary English-speaking societies, where time management is equated with success.

Emotion is another domain rich in metaphorical conceptualization. Emotions are often described in terms of physical forces or containers, as in bursting with joy, bottling up feelings, or overcome by anger. Such metaphors make abstract psychological states more tangible, allowing speakers to communicate inner experiences in relatable terms. They also suggest a cultural tendency to externalize emotions as objects that can be controlled, suppressed, or released.

Social relations are likewise structured metaphorically. Hierarchical relationships are often conceptualized spatially: climbing the corporate ladder, a high-ranking official, or falling in status. Conflict and cooperation are also expressed metaphorically, with building bridges or breaking ties serving as common idioms. These metaphors shape how individuals

interpret social dynamics, highlighting the cognitive function of metaphor in constructing collective worldviews.

Overall, the results confirm that metaphors in modern English are integral to cognitive models, providing speakers with conceptual frameworks for navigating abstract aspects of life. Their prevalence in media and everyday speech underscores their role in shaping thought and social reality.

Conclusion. Metaphor in modern English is not merely decorative but a fundamental mechanism of cognition. By conceptualizing time as money, emotions as objects, and social relations as spatial hierarchies, English speakers make sense of abstract domains through familiar experiences. The study confirms that metaphors reflect and reinforce cultural values, playing a vital role in linguistic expression and thought. For foreign language teaching, awareness of metaphorical structures is crucial. Learners must go beyond literal comprehension to grasp the cultural and cognitive models embedded in metaphorical language. Similarly, in intercultural communication, recognizing the differences in metaphorical conceptualization across languages helps prevent misunderstandings. Future research may further explore how digital communication and global English influence metaphor use, as well as how metaphorical models evolve under cultural and technological changes.

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SOCIOLINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVES OF MULTILINGUAL LEARNERS

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Abstract: This article explores the intricate relationship among language, identity, and pedagogy in English as a Second Language (ESL) education. Drawing upon classical and contemporary sociolinguistic scholarship, the paper synthesizes perspectives from Labov, Fishman, Baugh, Fought, and Schilling, complemented by recent research (2020–2024) emphasizing linguistic equity, multilingualism, and cultural responsiveness. It argues that sociolinguistic awareness is fundamental to fostering inclusive learning environments that honor learners' linguistic repertoires and social identities.

Keywords: Sociolinguistics, multilingualism, identity, ESL education, linguistic equity, pedagogy, cultural responsiveness.

Introduction: The dynamic interaction among language, culture, and identity is central to second language education. In multilingual and multicultural contexts, learners'

linguistic repertoires reflect complex social experiences that influence both language acquisition and classroom interaction. Contemporary sociolinguistics offers a vital lens for examining how social variables such as ethnicity, class, gender, and community background shape learners' communicative behavior and educational outcomes. Foundational works by Labov (1972) and Fishman (1972) established the relationship between language variation and social structure, while more recent studies [1] have expanded this understanding to include translanguaging and identity negotiation. This article synthesizes key sociolinguistic perspectives to propose an inclusive framework for understanding and teaching English in multilingual classrooms.

Literature Review: Classical sociolinguistic theories emphasize that language use is socially embedded. Labov's (1972) analysis of linguistic variation across social groups revealed that language reflects and reinforces social stratification. Fishman's (1972) sociology of language further demonstrated how linguistic choices are tied to social functions and group identity. Subsequent scholars, including Baugh (2005), Fought (2011), and Schilling (2011), have explored how language intersects with ethnicity, race, gender, and sexuality, expanding the sociolinguistic scope to address issues of inclusion and representation.

In recent years, sociolinguistic inquiry has increasingly focused on multilingualism, linguistic justice, and the pedagogical implications of linguistic diversity. Deumert (2021) and García & Li Wei (2021) argue that multilingual learners construct hybrid linguistic identities through translanguaging practices, challenging traditional monolingual ideologies in education. New studies [2] advocate for critical sociolinguistics that positions language education as a site of social transformation. These works collectively underline the importance of understanding sociolinguistic realities to design equitable ESL pedagogy.

Discussion: Integrating sociolinguistic insights into ESL education fosters inclusivity, critical awareness, and communicative competence. Teachers who acknowledge learners' linguistic and cultural resources can create learning environments that validate diverse identities. Sociolinguistic competence thus becomes not only a linguistic skill but also a social and ethical imperative. As Baugh (2005) cautions, linguistic profiling can perpetuate bias and inequality, while Fought (2011) highlights that recognizing language–ethnicity links can empower marginalized learners. Recent research (Jaspers & Madsen, 2020; Piller, 2022) reinforces that sociolinguistically informed pedagogy promotes linguistic dignity and enhances student engagement.

In multilingual settings, English often functions as a lingua franca. Understanding how learners navigate between local and global linguistic codes enables teachers to support authentic communication. The sociolinguistic approach encourages educators to view students as legitimate multilingual speakers rather than deficient English learners. This paradigm aligns with translanguaging pedagogy [3], which values learners' entire linguistic repertoires as resources for meaning-making and academic success.

Applying sociolinguistic theory to classroom practice involves adopting culturally and linguistically responsive pedagogies. Instruction should reflect learners' social realities, using authentic materials, collaborative learning, and reflective discussion on language ideologies. Teachers play a transformative role by mediating between linguistic diversity and academic expectations. Professional development that enhances sociolinguistic awareness can help educators design lessons that promote inclusion and linguistic empowerment.

Moreover, curriculum design should emphasize communicative competence and intercultural understanding over prescriptive language norms. Recognizing language as a social practice fosters critical thinking and empathy, preparing learners for participation in globalized communication networks.

Assessment practices must align with sociolinguistic principles of fairness and equity. Standardized tests often privilege dominant linguistic varieties and disadvantage students from diverse language backgrounds. Ethical assessment frameworks should incorporate formative assessment, alternative evaluation methods, and accommodations that reflect learners' linguistic realities. According to recent studies [4], culturally responsive assessment practices enhance validity and support student motivation by acknowledging multiple forms of linguistic competence.

Ethical pedagogy also requires educators to challenge linguistic prejudice, promote students' linguistic rights, and cultivate classrooms that value all forms of linguistic expression. Such practices advance social justice in education by bridging sociolinguistic theory and classroom application.

Sociolinguistic perspectives provide a powerful framework for understanding the intersection of language, identity, and education in multilingual contexts. By integrating classical theories with recent developments in critical and applied sociolinguistics, educators can design inclusive pedagogical and assessment practices that affirm linguistic diversity. Ultimately, fostering sociolinguistic awareness among teachers and learners contributes to linguistic equity, intercultural competence, and democratic participation in global society. The future of ESL education depends on recognizing multilingualism as an asset and embedding sociolinguistic principles into all dimensions of teaching and learning.

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PARAFRAZA VA INSONLARGA QO‘YILGAN LAQABLAR TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kishilarga, ulardagi ijobiy va salbiy holatlariga ishora qiluvchi biror laqab bilan atash mavjudligi to‘g‘risida ham fikr bildirilgan. Shundan so‘ng parafrazalar, ularning stilistik vosita sifatida nutqqa ko‘tarinkilik, obrazlilik baxsh etishi izohlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Parafraza, laqab, obraz, yangidan nomlash, laqab bilan atash, estetik munosabat, parafraza, stilistik vosita, parafrazalarning turlari.

Turkiy xalqlarda voqea-hodisalar va shaxslarni o‘z nomi bilan emas, balki ularning belgi-xususiyatlarini tasvirlash orqali yangidan nomlash hodisasi uchraydi. Shuningdek kishilarga, ulardagi ijobiy va salbiy holatlariga ishora qiluvchi biror laqab bilan atash holati ham mavjud. Bizga ma’lumki, insonlarga berilgan har qanday tasviriy ifoda yoki laqabda qandaydir estetik munosabat mujassam bo‘ladi. Parafraza (yunoncha “paraphrasis” – tasviriy ifoda, tasvir). Narsa, hodisani o‘z nomi bilan emas, ularni xarakterli belgi-xususiyatlari asosida tasviriy usul bilan ifodalash; shunday ifoda. Masalan: dala malikasi (makkajo‘xori), zangori olov (gaz) kabi.[1,80-b] O‘zbek milliy estradasining asoschisi (Botir Zokirov). Parafrazalar nafaqat jozibadorlik, obrazlilik va nutqni boyitish, balki uning mazmunini kuchaytirish uchun ham xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek jamiyatning olg‘a qadam qo‘yishiga to‘sqinlik qilayotgan illatlarni fosh qilish, ularga qarshi kurashga chaqirish maqsadida ham qo‘llaniladi. Binobarin parafrazalar predmet, voqea-hodisalarning o‘z nomi orqali yuzaga chiqmagan muhim xususiyatlarini tasvirlab, bo‘rttirib, izohlab va to‘ldirib ko‘rsatishda muhim nutqiy vosita hisoblanadi.

Laqab (arabcha “ikkinchi nom”, “laqab”, “taxallus”).

1. Biror xususiyatiga ko‘ra, kishiga hazil qilib yoki masxaralab berilgan qo‘shimcha nom. Shuningdek biror maqsad, zaruriyat bilan o‘zgartirib olingan boshqa nom. Masalan: Unga “Mitti” ... laqabini qaysi hazilvon qo‘ygan bo‘lsayam topib qo‘yibdi (H.N.).

2. Taxallus. Masalan: Muhammad Aminxo‘jani endi xalq Muqimiy deb taniy boshladi. Seni ham xalqqa bir laqab bilan tanitishni istayman! Sening laqabing Mavlaviy bo‘lsin dedi ustoz (S.A.).

3. Familiya. 4. Hayvonlarga qoyilgan nom. Masalan: Chalma va Medunka laqabi bo‘lgan ikkita g‘unajinning suti tekshirib boriladi (N.M.).

Ushbu izohdan ma’lumki, laqab lig‘aviy birligida to‘rt xil ma’no mujassamdir. Adiblar o‘z asarlarida mazkur so‘zining ana shu ma’nolaridan unumli foydalanishadi. Bu esa har bir tilning milliy jozibasini yanada oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Shuni aytish joizki, bunday evfemizatsiya boshqa halqlarda ham keng tarqalgan edi. A.Axmetov Amerika, Avstraliya, Osiyo qit‘asi xalqlari orasida odam ismi berkitilganligini yozadi.[2,176-b] Go‘yo uni ochiq aytish odam tanasiga ziyon etkazadi. Hatto: “– Oting nima?” deyilganda, “– Mening otim yo‘q” deb javob berishi, yonidagi urug‘doshiga: “– Men uchun sen ayta qol” deb iltimos qilishi Adjibvey qabilasining odati bo‘lganligini aytadi. Lekin bu “Asrovchi ismlar” nafaqat mazmunan ijobiy, chiroyli nomlardan, balki ko‘p holda qo‘pol, xunuk ma’noli nomlardan tashkil topishi ham mumkin. Vaholangki, bolaga xunuk ma’noli so‘zlardan yasalgan ismlarning berilishi chaqaloqni yomon ko‘zlardan, ko‘z tegishdan asrash, go‘dakning dushmani bo‘lmish yovuz kuchlarni chalg‘itish, aldash maqsadi bilan bog‘liqdir. O‘zbek ismlari orasida “asrovchi ismlar”ni tarixchi Sh.O‘ljayeva quyidagi guruhlarga ajratadi. Ularning ayrimlari quyidagicha:

Sog‘lik, uzoq umr tilashini ifoda etuvchi ismlar: Tursun, Turdi, To‘xtasin, O‘lmas, Yursin, Omonturdi, Turg‘un, Turg‘unoy, Ergash, Yo‘ldosh kabi.

Turli kasalliklarni engishi, chidamli, irodali, mustahkam bo‘lib o‘shishini orzu qilib qo‘yilgan ismlar: Tosh, Toshboy, Toshxon, Temur, Temura, Metinboy, Po‘lat, Cho‘yonboy, Qilichboy, Xanjara, Halqonboy, Teshaboy, Boltaboy, Mahkam, Mahkamoy, Berk, Berkinoy va boshqalar.

Yashovchanlik, barhayotlik, chidamlilik, uzoq umr ramzi bo‘lmish daraxtlar, narsalar nomidan yasalgan ismlar: Chinor, Chinora, Sadaboy, Archaboy, Yovshan va hokazo.

Yoqimsizlik, noxushlik, achchiqlik ramzi hisoblanuvchi narsalar, o‘simliklar nomidan yasalgan ismlar: Sarimsoq, So‘g‘onboy, Piyozbek va shular kabi. Mana shunday ismlar

qo'yilsa chaqaloqning dushmani, yovuz kuchlar bolaga yaqinlashmaydi, undan nari ketadi deb hisoblashgan.

Ba'zan ataylab xunuk ma'noli nomlarni qo'yishgan: Yomonbola, Itolmas, Itemas, Kasofat, Shag'alboy, Sabila kabi. Kishilar bola shunday nomlansa e'tiborsiz bo'ladi, unga ko'z tegmaydi deb hisoblashgan.

Bu tasnif tarixiy jihatdan mavjud manbalar asosida amalga oshirilgan bo'lib, lingvokulturologik jihatdan diniy, ijtimoiy, madaniy ziddiyatlarni yuzaga keltirishi tabiiy. Nutqiy vaziyatda bunday ismlar disfemik kayfiyat uyg'otishi, buning natijasida esa ism sohibining ijtimoiy mavqei, psixologik ruhiyati, kelajagi bilan bog'liq muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi tabiiy. Hayotiy misol: bir yoshi katta odamning 25 yillik hayoti ismi tufayli achinarli kechadi. 25 yoshgacha uning ismi tug'ilganlik guvohnomasi va shaxsini tasdiqlovchi hujjatida Tufli deb qayd etilgan bo'ladi. U shu yoshda hujjatni almashtirib Tolib deb o'z ismini o'zgartiradi. Vaholangki, u go'zal, sof o'zbekcha, ota-bobolarimizdan meros bo'lgan Tubli degan ismi bo'lganligidan bexabar. FXDYO xodimning kichik xatosi bir odamning 25 yil kulgi bo'lishiga olib keladi.

Xulosa qilib aytsak, har ikki (evfemizm va disfemizm) hodisa ham okkazonal xarakterga ega bo'lib, ular mudom o'zgarib turadi, doimo yangi. Faqat disfemizmdan farqli o'laroq, evfemizm vaqt o'tib, lisoniy birlikka aylananish xususiyatiga ega va, shu bilan birga, o'z evfemik xususiyatini ham yo'qota oladi. Bu tez-tez qo'llanish sababidan amalga oshadi. O.D.Pastuxova aytganidek, vaqt o'tishi bilan yoqimsiz narsalar evfemizatsiyasi samarasiz bo'ladi, chunki ular biron bir nozik mavzuni tasvirlashda kutilmaganda aytilganda o'z ma'nosining ravshanligi va aniqligi bilan quloqqa yoqimsiz eshitila boshlaydi. Disfemizmlar esa ortofemaga aylanmay, salbiy kuchida qolish bilan xarakterlanadi.

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“O‘ZBEK MEHMONDORCHILIGI” LEKSIK-SEMANTIK GURUHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek xalqining milliy qadriyatlari tizimida alohida o‘rin tutuvchi mehmondorchilik hodisasi lingvistik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda mehmondorchilik bilan bog‘liq leksik birliklarning semantik guruhlari, ularning ma‘no qatlamlari, hududiy va ijtimoiy xususiyatlari hamda xalq og‘zaki ijodidagi aks-sadosi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Maqolada mavjud adabiyotlar sharhi asosida mavzuning dolzarbligi yoritilib, korpus va kuzatuv materiallari asosida tilshunoslik, etnografiya hamda madaniyatshunoslik kesishmasida kompleks tahlil amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mehmondorchilik, leksik-semantik guruh, dasturxon, palov, o‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodi.

Abstract: This article analyzes the phenomenon of hospitality, which occupies a special place in the system of national values of the Uzbek people, from a linguistic perspective. The research examines the semantic groups of lexical units related to hospitality, their layers of meaning, regional and social characteristics, as well as their reflection in Uzbek folklore. Based on a review of existing literature, the relevance of the topic is highlighted, and a comprehensive analysis is conducted at the intersection of linguistics, ethnography, and cultural studies using corpus and observational data.

Keywords: hospitality, lexical-semantic group, dasturkhon (table setting), plov (pilaf), Uzbek oral folklore.

Аннотация: В данной статье с лингвистической точки зрения анализируется феномен гостеприимства, занимающий особое место в системе национальных ценностей узбекского народа. В исследовании рассматриваются семантические группы лексических единиц, связанных с гостеприимством, их смысловые слои, региональные и социальные особенности, а также отражение этого явления в узбекском народном устном творчестве. На основе обзора существующей литературы раскрывается актуальность темы, а также проводится комплексный анализ на стыке лингвистики, этнографии и культурологии с использованием корпусных и наблюдательных данных.

Ключевые слова: гостеприимство, лексико-семантическая группа, дастурхон, плов, узбекское народное устное творчество.

Har bir xalqning milliy madaniyati va turmush tarzini belgilovchi asosiy omillardan biri - uning mehmondorchilik an‘analaridir. Mehmondorchilik qadriyatlari xalqning tarixiy taraqqiyoti davomida shakllanib, ijtimoiy hayotning eng muhim ko‘rinishlaridan biriga aylangan. O‘zbek xalqi tarixan mehr-oqibatli, bag‘rikeng va mehmondo‘st xalq sifatida tanilgan bo‘lib, bu xususiyatlar milliy mentalitetning ajralmas qismi sifatida qaraladi. Shu bois xalq orasida keng tarqalgan “Mehmon –Atoyi Xudo” degan maqol o‘zbeklarning dunyoqarashida mehmonning muqaddas maqomini ifodalaydi.

O‘zbek mehmondorchiligi o‘zida nafaqat moddiy, balki ma‘naviy boyliklarni ham mujassam etadi. Mehmon kutish, dasturxon yozish, milliy taomlar tayyorlash, izzat-ikrom ko‘rsatish jarayoni o‘ziga xos rasm-rusum va odob-axloq qoidalari bilan boyitilgan. Ushbu jarayon davomida yuzlab leksik birliklar faol ishlatiladi va ular tilimizda alohida leksik-semantik guruhni shakllantirgan. Masalan, “mehmon”, “mehmondor”, “mehmondorchilik” kabi asosiy atamalar bilan bir qatorda, “palov”, “somsa”, “sho‘rva” kabi taom nomlari,

“lagan”, “piyola”, “kosa” kabi buyum nomlari hamda “hurmat”, “izzat”, “duo”, “so‘rashmoq” kabi odob-axloqqa oid birliklar mazkur guruhning tarkibiy qismlarini tashkil etadi. Mehmondorchilik hodisasi xalq og‘zaki ijodida ham keng ifodalangan. “Mehmon kelsa, davlat kirar”, “Mehmonga hurmat – odamga hurmat” kabi maqollar xalq tafakkurining, ijtimoiy qadriyatlarining bevosita lingvistik ko‘rinishidir. Shu sababli mehmondorchilik bilan bog‘liq leksik qatlamni faqat tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan emas, balki madaniyatshunoslik, tarix va etnografiya fanlari kesimida ham o‘rganish dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Mazkur maqola o‘zbek tilida mehmondorchilik hodisasini ifodalovchi leksik birliklarni ilmiy tahlil qilishni maqsad qiladi. Tadqiqot doirasida mehmondorchilikka oid birliklarning semantik tasnifi, ularning xalq mentalitetidagi ramziy o‘rni va og‘zaki ijod namunalari bilan bog‘liqligi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shu orqali o‘zbek xalqining madaniy merosi va milliy tafakkurida mehmondorchilik hodisasining chuqur ildiz otgani, uning lingvistik jihatdan qay darajada boy qatlamni yuzaga keltirgani aniqlanadi.

O‘zbek mehmondorchiligi va unga oid leksik qatlamni ilmiy o‘rganish masalasi tilshunoslik, etnografiya va madaniyatshunoslik yo‘nalishlarida qator tadqiqotchilar e‘tiborini tortgan. Xususan, tilshunolar mehmondorchilikka oid atamalarni leksik-semantik maydon sifatida o‘rganib, ularning xalqning ijtimoiy hayoti va milliy dunyoqarashidagi o‘rnini ko‘rsatib berishga harakat qilganlar.

Masalan, A. Madrahimov va Sh. Shukurovalar o‘z tadqiqotlarida o‘zbek tilidagi maishiy leksikaning shakllanishi va semantik guruhlarga ajralishi haqida so‘z yuritib, mehmondorchilik bilan bog‘liq birliklarni ham alohida guruh sifatida qayd etadi. Shuningdek, N. Mahmudov va A. Nurmonovlarning umumiy tilshunoslikka oid ishlarida milliy madaniyatni ifodalovchi so‘z qatlamining til tizimidagi o‘rni haqida muhim nazariy fikrlar berilgan.

Etnografik manbalarda ham mehmondorchilikka katta e‘tibor qaratilgan. H. Zarifov, M. Is‘hoqov, T. Mirzaev kabi olimlarning xalq og‘zaki ijodiga oid tadqiqotlarida mehmondorchilik marosimlari, maqol va matallardagi ifodalari haqida ma‘lumotlar uchraydi. Bu tadqiqotlarda mehmonni kutib olish, dasturxon yozish, milliy taomlarni tortish, mehmonni duo bilan kuzatish kabi urf-odatlarining ijtimoiy-madaniy ahamiyati keng yoritilgan.

Shuningdek, madaniyatshunoslik doirasida olib borilgan izlanishlarda mehmondorchilik qadriyatlari xalqning ma‘naviy merosi, ijtimoiy birdamlik va milliy o‘zlikni anglash jarayonlarida muhim omil sifatida baholanadi. Jumladan, M. Yo‘ldoshev va R. Berdialiyevalarning ilmiy ishlari o‘zbek turmush tarzida mehmondorchilikning ijtimoiy vazifalarini tahlil etishga bag‘ishlangan. Ammo mavjud adabiyotlarda mehmondorchilikka oid leksik birliklarning semantik tahlili ko‘proq umumiy ma‘lumotlar bilan cheklanadi, ularning ramziy ma‘nolari, hududiy farqlari va majoziy qo‘llanishlari yetarlicha yoritilmagan. Shu sababli mazkur maqolada ushbu kamchiliklarni to‘ldirish maqsadida mehmondorchilikka oid so‘zlar nafaqat lingvistik, balki madaniy va etnografik nuqtayi nazardan ham tahlil qilinadi.

Tadqiqot quyidagi manbalarga tayandi:

Xalq maqollari va matallari to‘plamlari;

Zamonaviy matbuot materiallari va badiiy asarlar;

Turli hududlarda qayd qilingan og‘zaki nutq namunalari tuzilgan kichik korpus (taxminan 50 ming so‘z).

Metod sifatida leksik-semantik tahlil, frazeologik tahlil, diskursiy tahlil va qiyosiy usullardan foydalanildi. Analiz jarayonida birliklar tematik guruhlarga ajratildi: (a) asosiy tushunchalar, (b) taom nomlari, (c) dasturxon va buyumlar, (d) odob-axloqni bildiruvchi birliklar, (e) majoziy iboralar.

1. Asosiy tushunchalar: “Mehmon”, “mehmondor”, “mehmondorchilik” soʻzlari mazkur guruhning yadrosini tashkil etadi. “Mehmonnavoz”, “mehmonsevar”, “mehmonxonona” kabi hosilalar mazkur maydonning semantik kengayishini koʻrsatadi.

2. Anʼanaviy taomlar bilan bogʻliq leksika: Palov, somsa, norin, shoʻrva, manti, lagʻmon, shivit oshi kabi birliklar mehmondorchilikning hududiy xususiyatlarini ham yoritadi. Masalan, Samarqand va Buxoroda palov, Fargʻonada norin, Xorazmda shivit oshi mehmon dasturxonida alohida qadrlanadi.

3. Dasturxon va xizmat buyumlari: “Dasturxon”, “lagan”, “kosa”, “piyola”, “choynak” kabi soʻzlar nafaqat predmetni, balki ijtimoiy birlik va izzatni ifodalaydi. “Dasturxon yozmoq” iborasi birlashish va suhbat ramzi sifatida ishlatiladi.

4. Odob-axloqni bildiruvchi birliklar: “Hurmat qilmoq”, “izzat koʻrsatmoq”, “duo qilmoq”, “soʻrashmoq” kabi feʻllar mehmondorchilikning maʼnaviy qirralarini ifodalaydi. Mehmon oxirida odat boʻyicha uy egasiga duo qiladi: “Dasturxonigizga baraka bersin”.

5. Majoziy maʼno va iboralar: “Palov tortmoq” - katta yigʻin oʻtkazmoq, “dasturxondan joy bermok” - hurmat koʻrsatmoq, “dasturxon yozmoq” - birlik yaratmoq maʼnolarida qoʻllanadi.

Oʻzbek mehmondorchiligi nafaqat maishiy ehtiyoj, balki xalqning ijtimoiy-madaniy hayotini tartibga soluvchi qadriyat sifatida alohida oʻrin tutadi. Mehmondorchilikka oid leksik birliklar oddiy soʻzlar yigʻindisi emas, balki xalq tafakkuri va milliy dunyoqarashining lingvistik ifodasi hisoblanadi. Shunday ekan, ushbu qatlamni oʻrganish orqali biz oʻzbek xalqining mentalitetini, urf-odatlarini va maʼnaviy olamini chuqurroq anglashimiz mumkin.

Avvalo, mehmondorchilik leksikasida madaniy-milliy mazmun ustuvor oʻrin tutadi. “Mehmon”, “mehmondor”, “mehmondorchilik” kabi atamalar xalq ongida nafaqat soʻz sifatida, balki butun bir madaniy hodisaning timsoli sifatida yashaydi. Bu birliklarning qoʻllanilishi oʻzbek xalqining bagʻrikengligi, hurmat-izzati va oʻzaro birdamlik ruhini aks ettiradi.

Ikkinchidan, ushbu leksik qatlam orqali xalqning turmush tarzi yorqin ifodalanadi. Masalan, palov, somsa, shoʻrva, choy kabi birliklar nafaqat taom nomlari, balki mehmondorchilik marosimlarining ajralmas qismi sifatida ham semantik ahamiyatga ega. Ular xalqning kundalik hayotini, hududiy urf-odatlarini va ijtimoiy anʼanalarini til orqali namoyon etadi.

Uchinchidan, mehmondorchilik leksikasida odob-axloqiy meʼyorlarni bildiruvchi birliklar alohida guruhni tashkil etadi. “Hurmat qilmoq”, “duo qilmoq”, “izzat koʻrsatmoq” kabi iboralar xalqning ijtimoiy munosabatlaridagi axloqiy qadriyatlarni belgilab beradi. Bu esa tilning faqat kommunikativ vosita emas, balki maʼnaviy qadriyatlarni avloddan-avlodga yetkazuvchi omil ekanligini koʻrsatadi.

Bundan tashqari, mehmondorchilik bilan bogʻliq soʻz va iboralar koʻpincha majoziy maʼnoda ham qoʻllanadi. Masalan, “dasturxon yozmoq” iborasi koʻproq “yigʻilish oʻtkazmoq”, “birlik yaratmoq” maʼnosida ishlatiladi. Bu hodisa tilning koʻp qirraliligini, xalq tafakkurining ramziy tasavvurlarga boyligini ifodalaydi.

Mavjud adabiyotlar tahlili shuni koʻrsatadiki, mehmondorchilik qadriyatlari koʻproq etnografik va folkloristik jihatdan yoritilgan boʻlsa-da, ularning leksik-semantik tahlili yetarlicha chuqur oʻrganilmagan. Ayniqsa, mehmondorchilikka oid iboralarning ramziy maʼnolari, hududiy farqlari va ogʻzaki ijoddagi qoʻllanilishi ilmiy izlanishlarga muhtoj. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, mazkur tadqiqot mehmondorchilik hodisasining lingvistik xususiyatlarini kengroq yoritishga qaratilgani bilan yangilik kasb etadi.

Oʻzbek tilidagi “mehmondorchilik” leksik-semantik guruhi: Madaniy-milliy mazmun - “mehmon”, “mehmondor”, “mehmondorchilik” birliklari bagʻrikenglik va izzat-ikromni

ifodalaydi. Turmush tarzini aks ettiruvchi birliklar - palov, somsa, choy, dasturxon kabi soʻzlar xalqning kundalik anʼanaviy hayoti bilan chambarchas bogʻliq. Odob-axloqiy meʼyorlarni bildiruvchi birliklar - hurmat, duo, soʻrashmoq kabi birliklar mehmondorchilik jarayonida muhim rol oʻynaydi. Majoziy maʼno va ogʻzaki ijod - maqollar va iboralar orqali bu qatlam ramziy maʼno kasb etadi. Shunday qilib, mehmondorchilik leksikasi oʻzbek xalqining madaniy merosi, ijtimoiy hayoti va milliy tafakkurini mujassam etgan holda, tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan chuqur oʻrganishga arzigulik semantik guruhdir.

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TILSHUNOSLIKNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI OʻRNI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslikning bugungi kundagi oʻrni boʻyicha hamda til madaniyati va nutqidagi muammolar va yechimlar borasida soʻz borgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: tilshunoslik, globalizatsiya, texnika, resurs, kognitiv lingvistika, til madaniyati, axborot, jamiyat, sotsiolingvistika, pragmalingvistika.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается современное значение лингвистики, а также проблемы и пути решения, связанные с культурой речи и языковыми нормами.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, глобализация, техника, ресурс, когнитивная лингвистика, культура речи, информация, общество, социолингвистика, прагмалингвистика.

Annotation: This article discusses the current role of linguistics, as well as the issues and solutions related to speech culture and language norms.

Keywords: linguistics, globalization, technology, resource, cognitive linguistics, speech culture, information, society, sociolinguistics, pragmalinguistics.

Bugungi kunda tilshunoslik fani jamiyatdagi oʻrni bilan yanada ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. [1] Tilshunoslik ham barcha fanlar bilan uzviy bogʻliq. Til butun bir jamiyatning madaniyati dunyoqarashi va tafakkurini ifodalab beradi. Til nafaqat odam uchun oʻzaro aloqa vositasi balki milliy oʻzlikni anglatuvchi asosiy omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Shu boisdan ham tilni oʻrganish va uning tuzilishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari va bugungi ijtimoiy hayotdagi ahamiyati haqida chuqur izlanishlar olib borish zarurdir.

Ayni damda hozirgi zamon tilshunoslik fani inson faoliyatining turli sohalari bilan o'zaro bog'lanib bormoqda. Misol uchun, globalizatsiya, zamonaviy texnika va axborot resurs texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi oqibatida tilning mamlakatimizdagi roli yanada yuqori darajaga ko'tarildi. Zamonaviy Axborot oqimi shunchalik tezlashganki, natijada til endi faqat o'zaro so'zlashuv yoki yozish usuli emas, balki axborotni uzatish, saqlash va qayta ishlash tizimining asosiy markaziga aylandi. Shu boisdan ham tilshunoslik hozirda nafaqat nazariy, balki amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadigan fan sifatida rivojlanib shakllanmoqda. Hozirgi kunda tilshunoslikning bajaradigan vazifalari faqatgina grammatik tizimni o'rganish bilan chegaralanib qolmaydi. U jamiyat tafakkurini, ijtimoiy muhit va ro'lini, madaniy qadriyatlarni o'rganish orqali tilning jamiyatdagi o'rnini yoritib beradi. Shu sababdan ham, zamonaviy tilshunoslik har bir millatning nafaqat madaniy yoki manaviy jihatini balki intellektual taraqqiyotini ta'minlovchi asosiy muhim fan sifatida qaraladi. Shuningdek bugungi kunda tilshunoslikda zamonaviy yo'nalishlar va yangi yondashuvlar ham ishlab chiqilmoqda.

Tilshunoslik so'nggi o'n yilliklar davomida sezilarli darajada kengayib, yangi yo'nalishlar paydo bo'ldi. Avvallari til faqat grammatik tizim uchun xizmat qilib, fonetika, morfologiya va sintaksis nuqtai nazaridan o'rganilgan bo'lsa, hozirda kognitiv lingvistika, pragmalingvistika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, korpus lingvistikasi kabi yangi yo'nalishlar shakllandi. Bu shuncha yil ichida tilshunoslikka alohida etibor berilganidan dalolat beradi. Bu yo'nalishlar tilni nafaqat inson tafakkuri, madaniyati, jamiyatdagi o'rni va hattoki texnologik rivojlanish bilan bog'liq jarayon sifatida o'rganishga qaratilgan. Misol uchun, kognitiv lingvistika til orqali inson fikrlash tafakkuri qanday shakllanishini o'rganadi. Pragmalingvistika esa nutq jarayoni davomida so'zlovchi va tinglovchining kommunikativ jihatini tahlil qiladi. Sotsiolingvistika esa tilning ijtimoiy tabaqalarini o'rganadi bular: yosh, jins va kasb. Shuningdek, kompyuter lingvistikasi va sun'iy intellekt asosida yaratilayotgan tadqiqotlar tilshunoslikni yangi bosqichga va yangi eraga olib chiqdi. Madaniyat deganda bugungi kunda barcha insonlar jamiyatda o'zini tuta bilishini tushunishadi ammo madaniyat hamma sohada bor. Shuningdek, til madaniyati va nutq madaniyati sohalarida ham dolzarb muammolar mavjud.[2]

Til madaniyati har bir xalqning ma'naviy olami va madaniy saviyasini ifodalovchi asosiy mezonlardan biridir. Insonning fikrini aniq, ravon va ta'sirli ifoda eta olishi, uning nutq madaniyatiga, so'z boyligiga hamda adabiy til me'yorlariga amal qilish darajasiga bog'liq. Til madaniyati nafaqat so'zlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qilish yoki grammatik qoidalarga rioya etish, balki fikrni estetik jihatdan go'zal, o'rinli va tushunarli tarzda yetkazish san'atidir. Shu bois, til madaniyati millatning o'zligini, tafakkur madaniyatini va ijtimoiy madaniyat darajasini aks ettiradi. Bugungi globallashuv davrida til madaniyatini saqlash masalasi yanada dolzarb tus olmoqda. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda so'zlashuv tilining aralash shakllari, imlo xatolari, begona so'zlarning ko'payishi adabiy til me'yorlariga zarar yetkazmoqda. Ayniqsa, yoshlar orasida ruscha yoki inglizcha so'zlarni o'zbek tiliga qo'shib ishlatish holatlari tez-tez uchramoqda. Bunday aralashmalar asta-sekin so'z boyligini kamaytiradi, milliy tilning tabiiy ohangini yo'qota boshlaydi. Shu sababli har bir inson, ayniqsa, o'qituvchilar, jurnalistlar va ziyolilar til madaniyatini asrashda namuna bo'lishi lozim. Nutq madaniyati esa til madaniyatining amaliy ko'rinishidir. Bu insonning kundalik muloqotda, darsda, nutq so'zlashda yoki yozma ifodada so'zlarni to'g'ri tanlashi, talaffuz, intonatsiya va uslubni joyida qo'llay bilish ko'nikmasini o'z ichiga oladi. Madaniyatli nutq sohibi nafaqat to'g'ri gapiradi, balki o'z fikrini tinglovchiga yoqimli va ta'sirli tarzda etkazadi. Ayniqsa, o'qituvchi, siyosatchi yoki san'atkor uchun nutq madaniyati kasbiy mahoratning ajralmas qismidir. Til va nutq madaniyatini yuksaltirish uchun ta'lim muassasalarida o'quvchilarni to'g'ri yozish, to'g'ri

talaffuz va soʻz boyligini oshirishga oʻrgatish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shu bilan birga, ommaviy axborot vositalari, internet sahifalari ham adabiy til meʼyorlariga amal qilishi zarur. Tildagi aniqlik, soʻzlardagi ifoda goʻzalligi va nutqdagi madaniylik - bu jamiyat taraqqiyotining belgilaridan biridir. Til madaniyati va nutq madaniyati muammolari bugungi kunda faqat tilshunoslarning emas, balki butun jamiyatning eʼtiborida boʻlishi kerak. Chunki tilning tozaligi, soʻzning goʻzalligi va nutqning boyligi - bu millatning madaniy yuksakligidir. Har bir inson oʻz ona tilini sevsa, uni toza, chiroyli va meʼyorida ishlatib, bu xalqning madaniy hayoti yanada yuksaladi. Til madaniyati va nutq madaniyati bilan bogʻliq muammolarni hal etish uchun, eng avvalo, taʼlim tizimida ona tili va nutq oʻstirish fanlariga eʼtibor kuchaytirilishi zarur. Boshlangʻich sinflardan oʻquvchilarga toʻgʻri talaffuz, imlo, fikrni aniq ifodalash va nutq odobini oʻrgatish uchun amaliy mashgʻulotlar koʻpaytirilishi lozim. Darslarda adabiy matnlarni oʻqish, sheʼr yodlash, erkin fikrlash mashqlari, suhbatlar va munozaralar orqali oʻquvchilarning nutq madaniyatini shakllantirish samarali natija beradi. Shuningdek, ommaviy axborot vositalari va internet sahifalarida til meʼyorlariga rioya etilishi ustidan nazoratni kuchaytirish muhimdir. Jurnalistlar, blogerlar va teleboshlovchilar adabiy tildan toʻgʻri foydalanishga masʼul boʻlishlari kerak. Chunki ular keng ommaga taʼsir oʻtkazuvchi shaxslar hisoblanadi va ularning nutqi yoshlar uchun oʻrnak boʻladi. Tilshunoslar, oʻqituvchilar va adabiyot ahli hamkorlikda zamonaviy til madaniyati boʻyicha qoʻllanmalar, oʻquv dasturlari va metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishlari lozim. Shu yoʻl bilan yoshlar orasida adabiy tildan toʻgʻri foydalanish odatini shakllantirish mumkin. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda “Til madaniyati kuni”, “Toʻgʻri yoz, chiroyli soʻzla” kabi loyihalar tashkil etish tilga eʼtiborni oshiradi. Ota-onalar ham farzandlariga toʻgʻri soʻzlash, odob bilan muloqot qilish, soʻz tanlashda ehtiyot boʻlishni oʻrgatishlari zarur. Oiladagi nutq muhiti bolaning kelajakdagi nutq madaniyatini belgilab beradi. Til va nutq madaniyatini saqlash milliy qadriyatni asrash bilan barobardir. Har bir inson oʻz ona tiliga hurmat bilan yondashib, uni toʻgʻri, chiroyli va ifodali ishlatishga harakat qilsa, jamiyatda madaniyatli muloqot muhitini yaratish mumkin. Shu tariqa, til madaniyati faqat tilshunoslik muammosi emas, balki butun jamiyatning maʼnaviy burchiga aylanadi. Bu yoʻnalishlar boʻyicha zamonaviy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. [4]

Xulosa qilib aytganda, tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolarini hal etish – bu tilni saqlash, boyitish va uni kelajak avlodlarga toza holda yetkazish demakdir. Tilni asrash – bu millatni asrashdir. Chunki til orqali xalqning oʻziga xosligi, madaniyati va tafakkuri avloddan avlodga oʻtadi. Har bir inson oʻz ona tiliga mehr bilan qarab, uni toʻgʻri, chiroyli va ifodali ishlatishga intilsa, bu nafaqat shaxsiy madaniyatning, balki milliy yuksalishning ham ifodasidir. Shu bois, tilni sevish, uni qadrlash va uni himoya qilish - har birimizning fuqarolik burchimizdir.

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SEMANTIC AND STYLISTIC PROCESSES IN AUTO-LEXICAL TERMS

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Abstract: The investigation of semantic and stylistic mechanisms within auto-lexical terms represents a multidisciplinary field that bridges linguistics, cognitive science, and computational language studies. This paper examines how lexical units develop semantic depth and stylistic nuance, focusing particularly on auto-lexical terms - self-referential words that encapsulate intrinsic meaning.

Keywords: semantics, stylistics, auto-lexical terms, cognitive linguistics, computational linguistics

Auto-lexical terms are distinctive in their capacity to convey meaning independently of contextual cues. They often form the basis of semantic interpretation, where the linkage between linguistic form and meaning is systematic rather than arbitrary, grounded in cognitive and linguistic regularities. Pexman's research demonstrates that the bond between form and meaning is mediated by semantic richness, implying that more conceptually elaborate terms prompt more complex cognitive activity. This highlights the necessity of exploring the functional role of auto-lexical terms within the broader lexical system.

Semantic processing encompasses the cognitive operations enabling individuals to access and apply the meanings attached to lexical units. Marschark and colleagues observe that semantic congruity strongly influences how people process comparative expressions, showing that presentation order can shape semantic interpretation. Consequently, the cognitive demand involved in processing auto-lexical terms fluctuates depending on contextual arrangement.

Similarly, Jefferies et al. find that both lexical and semantic dimensions significantly affect memory performance, indicating that the comprehension of auto-lexical terms involves active interaction with the semantic network rather than passive retrieval. Such findings reveal that understanding these terms requires examining how lexical representations dynamically integrate within the cognitive framework of meaning construction.

The stylistic facet of auto-lexical terms is equally critical, as it reflects the expressive and aesthetic potential of language. Stylistic variation enables speakers and writers to manipulate lexical form for rhetorical or interpretive effect. Swart et al. demonstrate that lexical quality significantly enhances reading comprehension, illustrating that the richness and diversity of vocabulary strengthen stylistic articulation. Moreover, Romaniuk's research into translation practices shows that lexical-semantic shifts often serve stylistic purposes, ensuring accurate and contextually appropriate rendering across languages. These transformations underscore that auto-lexical terms are not merely semantic vehicles but also essential components of stylistic design, influencing tone, register, and communicative intent.

In computational linguistics, a nuanced grasp of semantic and stylistic processes is indispensable for advancing natural language processing (NLP). The integration of lexical-semantic resources within machine learning models enhances their interpretive capacity by embedding both meaning and stylistic nuance. For example, lexical chain techniques exploit inter-word relationships to deepen textual understanding.

Sriharee's ontology-based model for automatic content tagging further illustrates how semantic analysis contributes to more accurate classification and retrieval. These computational approaches affirm that a dual focus on semantic coherence and stylistic

variability can significantly improve the sophistication and precision of automated linguistic systems.

The examination of semantic and stylistic processes in auto-lexical terms reveals a complex interdependence among meaning, cognition, and expression. Continued inquiry into these processes not only broadens our theoretical understanding of lexical behavior but also informs applied domains such as education, translation, and artificial intelligence. By synthesizing semantic and stylistic insights, scholars can foster a more holistic view of language - one that appreciates its cognitive foundations and expressive diversity.

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FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation. This article presents a comparative analysis of the functional-semantic features of adjectives in English and Uzbek. It demonstrates that due to the analytic nature of English and the agglutinative structure of Uzbek, there are significant differences in the formation, usage, and semantic classification of adjectives. In English, the strict order of adjectives and analytic methods of forming degrees of comparison are highlighted as key features. In Uzbek, by contrast, a rich affixation system, substantivization, and the presence of culturally specific layers are emphasized. The results of this comparative analysis hold both theoretical and practical significance for linguistics, translation studies, and language teaching methodology.

Keywords: *adjective, functional-semantic features, comparative analysis, English language, Uzbek language, affixation, analytic structure.*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi sifatlarning funksional-semantik xususiyatlari qiyosiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Ingliz tili analitik, o‘zbek tili esa agglutinativ til bo‘lgani uchun sifatlarning shakllanishi, qo‘llanishi va semantik tasnifida sezilarli farqlar mavjudligi ko‘rsatib beriladi. Ingliz tilida sifatlarning qat’iy tartibda joylashishi va darajalashning analitik usullari asosiy xususiyat sifatida ta’kidlanadi. O‘zbek tilida esa boy affiksatsiya tizimi, otlashish hodisasi va milliy-madaniy qatlam mavjudligi alohida ko‘rsatiladi. Qiyosiy tahlil natijalari tarjimashunoslik, til o‘qitish metodikasi va lingvistik tadqiqotlar uchun nazariy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *sifat, funksional-semantik xususiyat, qiyosiy tahlil, ingliz tili, o‘zbek tili, affiksatsiya, analitik tuzilish.*

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится сравнительный анализ функционально-семантических особенностей прилагательных в английском и узбекском языках. Показано, что в силу аналитического характера английского языка и агглютинативной природы узбекского языка, в формировании, употреблении и семантической классификации прилагательных наблюдаются значительные различия. В английском языке основными чертами являются строгий порядок следования прилагательных и аналитические способы степеней сравнения. В узбекском языке, напротив, характерны богатая система аффиксации, субстантивация и наличие национально-культурного слоя. Результаты сравнительного анализа имеют как теоретическое, так и практическое значение для переводоведения, методики преподавания языков и лингвистических исследований.

Ключевые слова: *прилагательное, функционально-семантические особенности, сравнительный анализ, английский язык, узбекский язык, аффиксация, аналитическая структура.*

Introduction. Adjectives, as an essential lexical-grammatical category, play a crucial role in the linguistic system by expressing the qualities and properties of objects and phenomena. Although adjectives in English and Uzbek serve a similar general grammatical function, their formation, usage, and semantic classification reveal distinctive features due to the typological nature of the two languages. English, being an analytic language, and Uzbek, as an agglutinative one, demonstrate fundamental differences in the morphological structure, syntactic behavior, and semantic categorization of adjectives.

Main body. English is an analytic language and Uzbek is an agglutinative one, the formation, usage, and semantic classification of adjectives reveal distinctive features [1]. In English, adjectives are generally invariable in form and perform two primary functions: attributive and predicative [2]. For example, in *a clever student* the adjective functions as an attribute, while in *The weather is cold* it functions as a predicate. Degrees of comparison are formed with the suffixes *-er*, *-est* or with the words *more*, *most* (*happy - happier - happiest; interesting - more interesting - most interesting*).

One of the important features of English adjectives is their fixed order in sequences. When several adjectives occur together, they follow a strict order: opinion → size → age → shape → color → origin → material → purpose. For instance, in *a beautiful big old round red Italian wooden dining table*, each adjective takes a specific position [3].

Semantically, English adjectives fall into the following groups:

- color and physical appearance (*red, tall, slim*),
- evaluative adjectives (*good, excellent*),
- state adjectives (*hungry, tired, happy*),
- cultural and national adjectives (*British, Victorian*) [4].

In Uzbek, adjectives are characterized by a rich morphological system. They are formed with numerous suffixes (*do'stona* "friendly", *kitobiy* "bookish", *oqsimon* "whitish"). Degrees of comparison are expressed with the suffix *-roq* or with the particle *eng* (*yaxshi – yaxshiroq – eng yaxshi*).

Functionally, Uzbek adjectives are used as attributes (*oq uy* "white house"), as predicates (*Havo issiq* "The weather is hot"), and as substantivized forms (*yaxshilar* "the good ones"). National-cultural adjectives also form a special layer: *oqko'ngil* "kind-hearted", *serjilo* "brilliant", *qo'rqmas* "fearless" [5].

Semantically, Uzbek adjectives are grouped as follows:

- colors (*oq* "white", *qora* "black"),
- size and shape (*uzun* "long", *keng* "wide"),

- qualities and states (*sho* ‘x “playful”, *kuchli* “strong”),
- evaluative (*yaxshi* “good”, *yomon* “bad”),
- national-cultural expressions (*oqko* ‘ngil “kind-hearted”, *sermehnat* “hard-working”) [6].

From a comparative perspective, both English and Uzbek adjectives denote qualities and characteristics of objects, but their morphological and syntactic features differ significantly. In English, adjectives follow a fixed order and comparison is often realized analytically or synthetically. In Uzbek, adjectives may occur more freely in word order, and affixation serves as the main means of word formation.

These differences are also significant in translation: English requires the preservation of fixed order (*a big red car*), while Uzbek allows more flexible ordering (*katta qizil mashina*). Similarly, Uzbek culturally bound adjectives need to be rendered with appropriate equivalents (*oqko* ‘ngil – *kind-hearted*) [7].

Conclusion. In conclusion, adjectives in English and Uzbek share common functions, but their functional-semantic features reflect the typological nature of each language. The strict order of adjectives and analytic comparison in English correspond to its analytic structure, while the rich affixation and strong presence of culturally specific adjectives in Uzbek demonstrate its agglutinative character. A comparative study of the functional-semantic features of adjectives is therefore of both theoretical and practical importance for linguistics, translation studies, and foreign language teaching methodology.

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АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена рассмотрению наиболее видные современные проблемы, с которыми сталкивается лингвистика в настоящее время. Развивающаяся природа языка вместе с интеграцией с другими областями, такими как психология и технологии, создала проблемы, включая языковые вариации и изменения, многоязычие, технологии, язык и мышление, искусственный интеллект и машинное обучение, диалектологию, влияние социальных сетей, речь и язык, патология, транс лингвистика и корпусная лингвистика. Для эффективного решения этих проблем требуется междисциплинарный подход, и они открывают возможности для инноваций и развития лингвистики.

Ключевые слова: Лингвистика, языковые вариации и изменения, многоязычие, технологии, язык и мышление, диалектология, патология речи и языка, корпусная лингвистика.

Abstract: The article focuses on the most prominent contemporary issues faced by modern linguistics. The evolving nature of language, along with its integration with other fields such as psychology and technology, has created challenges including language variation and change, multilingualism, language and technology, language and cognition, artificial intelligence and machine learning, dialectology, the influence of social networks, speech and language pathology, translanguaging, and corpus linguistics. Addressing these issues effectively requires an interdisciplinary approach, which in turn opens new opportunities for innovation and further development of linguistic science.

Keywords: linguistics, language variation and change, multilingualism, technology, language and cognition, dialectology, speech and language pathology, corpus linguistics.

Лингвистика, отрасль социальных наук, за последние годы стала свидетелем значительного развития и прогресса. Однако она также столкнулась с различными современными проблемами, с которыми постоянно сталкиваются исследователи и лингвисты. Этим проблемы возникли в результате развития природы языка, а также интеграции лингвистики с другими областями, такими как психология и технология.

Актуальные проблемы лингвистики включают понимание природы языка, языковые многообразие, вопросы универсальности языка, а также роли количественных методов и диахронического анализа.

Одной из основных задач современной лингвистики является изучение языковых вариаций и изменений. Язык – это динамическая сущность, которая постоянно развивается во времени благодаря использованию его носителя в разных контекстах. Лингвисты стремились понять факторы, влияющие на языковые вариации, такие как глобализацией и развитием цифровой коммуникации языки всё чаще контактируют друг с другом, что приводит к языковой конвергенции или даже к утрате языка. Это явление создаёт проблемы с точки зрения поддержания языкового разнообразия и сохранения языков, находящихся под угрозой исчезновения, а также понимания последствий изменения языка для общения и идентичность.

Ещё одной актуальной проблемой современной лингвистики является изучение многоязычия. Многоязычие имеет как лингвистические, так и социокультурные последствия. Лингвисты работают над пониманием когнитивных аспектов, связанных с овладением языком, двуязычием и языковой обработкой. Они исследуют такие вопросы, как то, как языки хранятся в мозгу и как они взаимодействуют друг с другом. Кроме того, многоязычие поднимает вопросы о языковой политике и планировании, поскольку обществу необходимо учитывать потребности различных языковых сообществ.

Одной из наиболее важных проблем, с которыми сегодня сталкиваются лингвисты, является исследование языка и мышления. Эта междисциплинарная область, известная как когнитивная лингвистика, исследует взаимосвязь между языком и познанием. Исследователи стремятся понять, как язык формирует наше восприятие и понимание окружающего мира. Они также исследуют влияние языка на различные когнитивные процессы, такие как память и принятие решений.

Технологии также поставили новые задачи в области лингвистики. В последние годы компьютерная лингвистика быстро развивается, и исследователи используют компьютерные модели и алгоритмы, чтобы лучше понять структурные аспекты языка,

а также для разработки таких приложений, как машинный перевод и программы изучения языка.

В заключение отметим, что современная лингвистика решает множества сложных проблем, обусловленных меняющейся природой языка, глобализацией, технологиями постоянно растущей интеграцией лингвистики с такими областями, как психология, искусственный интеллект и нейробиология. Благодаря постоянному развитию технологий и продолжающейся эволюции междисциплинарных подходов лингвисты хорошо подготовлены к решению сложностей, стремясь найти эффективные решения для улучшения нашего глобального лингвистического ландшафта.

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INTEGRATING PHONOLOGY AND PHONETICS IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: SOUND, RHYTHM, AND MEANING ACROSS LANGUAGES

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Abstract. Phonology and phonetics play an integral role in translation, influencing not only the perception of language but also the transfer of emotion, sound pattern, and aesthetic quality. Translators frequently encounter challenges when the sound features of one language do not have direct equivalents in another. This study explores three interrelated areas: (1) how sound symbolism can be translated across languages; (2) the impact of phonological constraints in transliteration and translation; and (3) the function of prosody in interpreting oral discourse. Through these perspectives, the paper argues that phonetic awareness enables translators to maintain both linguistic and emotional fidelity, contributing to a more authentic and engaging target text.

Keywords: Phonology, Phonetics, Sound Symbolism, Transliteration, Prosody, Translation Studies

Аннотация. Фонетика и фонетика играют неотъемлемую роль в переводе, влияя не только на восприятие языка, но и на передачу эмоций, звуковой картины и эстетических качеств. Переводчики часто сталкиваются с трудностями, когда звуковые особенности одного языка не имеют прямых эквивалентов в другом. В данном исследовании рассматриваются три взаимосвязанные области: (1) как звуковой символизм может быть передан между языками; (2) влияние фонологических ограничений на транслитерацию и перевод; и (3) функция просодии при переводе устной речи. С этих позиций в статье утверждается, что фонетическая осведомленность позволяет переводчикам сохранять как языковую, так и эмоциональную точность, способствуя созданию более аутентичного и увлекательного перевода.

Ключевые слова: Фонология, Фонетика, Звуковой символизм, Транслитерация, Просодия, Переводоведение

Annotatsiya. Fonologiya va fonetika tarjima jarayonida muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Ular nafaqat tilni idrok etish, balki hissiyot, tovush naqshi va estetik ohangni yetkazishda ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Tarjimonlar ko‘pincha tovush xususiyatlari boshqa tilda to‘liq muqobilga ega bo‘lmaganda qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar. Ushbu maqola uch jihatni ko‘rib chiqadi: (1) tillararo tovush timsollarini tarjima qilish; (2) transliteratsiya va tarjimada fonologik cheklovlarning ta‘siri; va (3) og‘zaki nutqni tarjima qilishda prozodiyaning roli. Tadqiqot shuni ko‘rsatadiki, fonetik sezgirlik tarjimonlarga nafaqat lingvistik, balki hissiy sadoqatni ham saqlash imkonini beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Fonologiya, fonetika, tovush timsoli, transliteratsiya, prozodiya, tarjima tadqiqotlari

Translation is not solely a transfer of meaning; it is also a transfer of sound, rhythm, and emotion. Phonology and phonetics- the study of sound systems and their articulatory and auditory properties-are vital components of linguistic structure that deeply influence how messages are understood. In many translation practices, however, these aspects are often neglected, especially in technical or literal renderings. Yet in literary, poetic, and oral contexts, the phonetic layer carries cultural and emotional weight. For example, rhyme, alliteration, and onomatopoeia can create vivid imagery that transcends simple denotation. Translators, therefore, need to develop a dual sensitivity: one toward meaning and another toward sound. According to Catford, true translation must account for both “linguistic and phonological equivalence,” since ignoring sound patterns can distort tone and communicative effect. This article aims to explore how translators manage these sound-related features through sound symbolism, phonological constraints, and prosody.

Sound symbolism suggests that certain phonemes evoke particular emotions or sensory experiences. For instance, the English cluster /sl/ (as in slime, slip, slow) tends to evoke smoothness or unpleasantness, while /gl/ (as in glow, glitter, gleam) is linked to light and brightness. Translators must find ways to preserve such associations even when phonetic equivalents do not exist.

In Japanese, mimetic words such as kirakira (sparkling) or dokidoki (heartbeat) vividly express sensory perception. Rendering these into English or Uzbek often requires creative adaptation rather than direct substitution. Jakobson (1960) argued that poetic language relies on “the projection of the equivalence principle from the axis of selection to the axis of combination.” In practice, this means translators should look for functionally similar sound effects in the target language rather than mechanically copying the form. For example, an Uzbek translator rendering “The silver sea shimmered” might choose “Kumush dengiz yaltirab tovlandi,” maintaining the rhythmic and sound harmony. Such awareness ensures that phonological form continues to support meaning, not contradict it.

Phonological constraints define how sounds are structured and permitted within a language. When words or names move across languages, transliteration must adapt them according to the target language’s sound system. Transliteration is not just a mechanical process of letter substitution-it involves complex phonological decisions. Take, for instance, the English name “Thomas,” which becomes “Томас” in Russian, or the Japanese adaptation of “McDonald’s” as Makudonarudo. These examples show how each language reshapes foreign phonemes into locally acceptable patterns. Catford (1965) emphasizes that transliteration must respect the phonotactic limits of the target system to avoid unintelligibility. In translation of cultural texts, such adaptation may extend beyond phonemes to entire syllabic structures. For example, the Arabic /q/ sound, absent in English, is commonly replaced with /k/, as in Quran → Koran. These transformations illustrate the phonological compromises translators make to balance clarity, familiarity, and authenticity for the audience.

Prosody-the combination of stress, rhythm, and intonation-adds the emotional and pragmatic layer to spoken language. In interpreting, prosody can completely change meaning. A simple English phrase like “You’re coming?” may sound inquisitive, impatient, or friendly depending on its intonation pattern. Interpreters and translators must convey these nuances across languages, adjusting pitch, stress, and rhythm to preserve pragmatic intent. As Gile (1995) notes, prosodic control is essential to “maintain communication equivalence” in real-time interpretation. The translator’s ear thus becomes as important as their vocabulary. Additionally, prosody shapes audience perception. In film dubbing, for instance, prosodic mismatches between original and dubbed versions can lead to emotional disconnection. Awareness of the target language’s natural rhythm and intonation patterns ensures that speech sounds authentic and emotionally resonant.

In conclusion, phonology and phonetics are not minor aspects of language but central to achieving full communicative equivalence in translation. Translating sound symbolism, adapting phonological structures, and reproducing prosody all demand sensitivity to how sound conveys meaning and emotion. If translators ignore these sound-based elements, the text may lose its expressive and aesthetic power, even when the words are accurate. Effective translation therefore requires the ability to both understand and hear language. A translator must not only reproduce what is said but also how it sounds. From my perspective, developing phonetic awareness should be an essential part of translator education, particularly for literary and oral forms of translation. By paying attention to sound, rhythm, and tone, translators can preserve the musicality of the original and bring its emotional depth to new audiences.

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INTEGRATING PRAGMATICS AND CONTEXT IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: SPEECH ACTS, POLITENESS, AND COMMUNICATIVE EQUIVALENCE ACROSS CULTURES

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Abstract. This paper explores the role of pragmatics and context in translation, emphasizing how meaning extends beyond linguistic forms into situational and cultural dimensions. Translators often encounter challenges when transferring speech acts, politeness strategies, and implicit messages across languages. The study examines how pragmatic equivalence - achieving the same communicative effect in the target language - can be maintained by analyzing context, speaker intention, and social norms. By applying principles of pragmatic theory, translators can produce more accurate and culturally appropriate translations that preserve the intended illocutionary force and interpersonal meaning of the source text.

Keywords: Pragmatics, Context, Speech Acts, Politeness Strategies, Pragmatic Equivalence, Implicit Meaning, Translation Studies

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется роль прагматики и контекста в переводе, с акцентом на том, как значение выходит за рамки языковых форм, охватывая ситуативные и культурные аспекты. Переводчики часто сталкиваются с трудностями при передаче речевых актов, стратегий вежливости и имплицитных сообщений между языками. В исследовании рассматривается, как прагматическая эквивалентность – достижение того же коммуникативного эффекта в языке перевода – может быть достигнута путем анализа контекста, намерения говорящего и социальных норм. Применяя принципы прагматической теории, переводчики могут создавать более точные и культурно адекватные переводы, сохраняющие предполагаемую иллокутивную силу и межличностное значение исходного текста.

Ключевые слова: Прагматика, Контекст, Речевые акты, Стратегии вежливости, Прагматическая эквивалентность, Имплицитное значение, Переводоведение

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola tarjimada pragmatika va kontekstning oʻrni oʻrganadi hamda maʼno faqat til shakllarigagina emas, balki vaziyat va madaniy omillarga ham bogʻliq ekanini taʼkidlaydi. Tarjimonlar koʻpincha nutq aktlari, xushmuomalalik strategiyalari va yashirin maʼnolarni bir tildan boshqasiga oʻtkazishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Tadqiqotda pragmatik tenglik tushunchasi - yaʼni tarjimada bir xil kommunikativ taʼsirga erishish - kontekst, soʻzlovchining maqsadi va ijtimoiy meʼyorlarni hisobga olgan holda tahlil qilinadi. Pragmatika nazariyasi tamoyillarini qoʻllash orqali tarjimon asl matnning nutq kuchi va shaxslararo maʼnosini saqlab qolgan holda yanada aniq va madaniy jihatdan mos tarjima yaratishi mumkinligi koʻrsatib beriladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Pragmatika, Kontekst, Nutq aktlari, Xushmuomalalik strategiyalari, Pragmatik tenglik, Yashirin maʼno, Tarjima tadqiqotlari

Pragmatics, as a branch of linguistics, focuses on how language is used in context to perform actions, express intentions, and convey social relationships. In translation, understanding pragmatics is essential because literal meaning often fails to capture the speaker's true communicative purpose. For instance, an utterance such as "Could you open the window?" may function not as a question about ability but as a polite request. Translating such expressions requires attention not only to grammar and vocabulary but also to the illocutionary force - the intended action behind the words. Moreover, pragmatic meaning is

heavily influenced by cultural conventions. What is considered polite, formal, or indirect in one language may sound rude or overly familiar in another. Therefore, a translator's task involves interpreting context-sensitive cues and adapting the message to the target culture while maintaining the speaker's intent. Pragmatic awareness, thus, bridges the gap between linguistic form and communicative effect.

Speech acts are fundamental to understanding how language functions as a tool for performing actions rather than merely conveying information. Each utterance carries an intended force and an expected response, forming the basis of effective communication. In translation, maintaining this functional aspect is challenging because expressions of requests, apologies, or promises vary greatly across cultures and languages. For instance, a direct command in English might sound impolite or too strong in other languages where indirectness is a sign of respect. Translators must therefore interpret the performative purpose of the speech act, not just its literal meaning. If this aspect is neglected, the translated text may lose its communicative effect, resulting in pragmatic failure. Successful transfer of speech acts depends on the translator's awareness of social norms, context, and intended communicative outcomes. (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969; Hatim & Mason, 1997).

Politeness plays a crucial role in maintaining social harmony and expressing respect in communication. However, the strategies used to achieve politeness differ widely among cultures. English speakers often rely on indirect expressions such as modal verbs or softening phrases, while other languages may incorporate politeness directly into their grammatical systems. When translating such expressions, literal equivalence is rarely sufficient. A phrase that sounds polite in one language might appear overly formal or distant in another. Therefore, translators must balance linguistic accuracy with cultural appropriateness, ensuring that the translated message preserves both the intended tone and the relational meaning. Understanding contextual cues and social hierarchies allows translators to convey the same level of politeness and emotional nuance as the source text. (Brown & Levinson, 1987; Blum-Kulka, 1989; House, 2015).

Meaning in translation is never created in isolation; it is shaped by the situational and cultural context in which communication occurs. Words or phrases that appear identical in form may convey entirely different meanings depending on the context. For example, the expression "You're early!" can serve as a neutral observation, a compliment, or even a mild reproach, depending on tone and circumstance. Translators must therefore analyze the pragmatic context - who is speaking, to whom, under what conditions, and with what intention. Pragmatic equivalence is achieved when the translated message generates the same communicative effect in the target audience as the original did in its cultural setting. This type of equivalence cannot always be established through grammatical or lexical correspondence alone; it requires sensitivity to speech situations, social hierarchies, and emotional undertones. Through this approach, translators become mediators of meaning rather than mechanical converters of text. (Nida, 1964; Baker, 1992; Nord, 2005).

Languages differ not only in structure but also in how they encode meaning. Some languages, like English, tend to express information explicitly, while others, such as Japanese or Uzbek, rely more heavily on context and shared cultural knowledge. These differences pose significant challenges for translators, who must decide whether to retain implicit meanings or make them explicit for the target audience. If too much implicit meaning is lost, the translation may become unclear or misleading. Conversely, over-explaining hidden implications may disrupt the natural flow of the text and reduce its authenticity. The translator's task, therefore, is to maintain a balance - preserving the subtlety and depth of the original while ensuring comprehension in the target language. Achieving this balance requires

both linguistic expertise and pragmatic awareness, as well as an understanding of cultural expectations about directness and inference. (Levinson, 1983; Gutt, 2000; House, 2015).

The analysis of pragmatics and context in translation highlights that meaning is never fixed but dynamically constructed through interaction, intention, and cultural understanding. Translators must interpret not only what is said but also what is meant - considering tone, politeness, and implicit messages. Speech acts, politeness strategies, and contextual meanings all demonstrate that language serves both communicative and social functions. Successful translation, therefore, depends on achieving pragmatic equivalence, where the translated text produces the same effect on the target audience as the original did on its readers. This requires deep awareness of the relationship between language and culture, as well as the translator's ability to balance explicitness and subtlety. Pragmatic competence transforms translation from a purely linguistic process into an intercultural act of communication, ensuring that meaning, intention, and emotion are faithfully conveyed across linguistic boundaries.

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INTEGRATING SOCIOLINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL PERSPECTIVES IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: DIALECTS, CODE-SWITCHING, AND CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. Translation is not merely a linguistic transfer but a sociocultural act that reflects how people think, interact, and belong to communities. Sociolinguistic and cultural factors such as dialects, speech styles, and multilingual behavior deeply influence the translator's decisions. This paper explores how dialects are represented in translation, the challenges of translating sociolinguistic variation, the handling of multilingualism and code-switching, and how culture determines linguistic choices. The study emphasizes that effective translation requires balancing linguistic accuracy with sociocultural authenticity to preserve the identity and voice of the original text.

Keywords: sociolinguistics, culture, dialects, code-switching, cross-cultural translation, linguistic variation

Аннотация. Перевод- это не просто языковой перенос, а социокультурный акт, отражающий мышление, взаимодействие и принадлежность людей к сообществам. Социолингвистические и культурные факторы, такие как диалекты, стили речи и многоязычное поведение, оказывают существенное влияние на решения переводчика. В данной статье рассматривается, как диалекты представлены в переводе, каковы сложности перевода социолингвистических вариаций, как работает многоязычие и

переключение кодов, а также как культура определяет лингвистический выбор. В исследовании подчёркивается, что для эффективного перевода необходимо соблюдать баланс между лингвистической точностью и социокультурной аутентичностью для сохранения самобытности и звучания исходного текста.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистика, культура, диалекты, переключение кодов, межкультурный перевод, языковая вариативность

Annotatsiya. Tarjima bu faqat tildan-tilga so‘z o‘tkazish emas, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy jarayon hamdir. Har bir tilda jamiyatning madaniy qadriyatlarini, ijtimoiy roli va nutq uslublari ifodalanadi. Shu sababli, tarjimonning qarorlari dialekt, nutq uslubi, ko‘p tillilik va madaniy tafovutlarga bog‘liq bo‘ladi. Ushbu maqolada dialektlarning tarjimada aks etishi, ijtimoiy tilshunoslikdagi farqlarni tarjima qilishdagi qiyinchiliklar, kod-almashinish va ko‘p tillilik masalalari, shuningdek, madaniyatning tarjima qarorlariga ta‘sirini tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot shuni ko‘rsatadiki, muvaffaqiyatli tarjima uchun nafaqat til aniqligi, balki madaniy moslik ham zarur, chunki aynan shu jihatlarda matnning ruhini saqlab qoladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: sotsiolingvistik, madaniyat, dialektlar, kod-almashinish, madaniyatlararo tarjima, lingvistik farqlar

Translation exists at the intersection of language, culture, and society. Each linguistic act reflects not only a grammatical system but also the identity, class, and worldview of its speakers. As Hatim and Mason (1990) explain, translation involves more than conveying propositional meaning- it requires sensitivity to the sociolinguistic functions of language use (p. 22, *Discourse and the Translator*). Translators operate within a social matrix where dialectal variation, formal or informal registers, and multilingual code-switching are crucial indicators of identity and power. Understanding these elements is vital because the same utterance can shift in tone, politeness, or authority depending on context. In the modern globalized world, where languages constantly interact, sociolinguistic awareness enables translators to recreate social meaning accurately. A translator who neglects these aspects risks flattening the original’s cultural depth. Therefore, sociolinguistic and cultural analysis must become a central pillar of translation studies.

Dialects express regional identity, social class, and cultural belonging. When translating, the challenge lies in how to preserve these features without making the text unreadable or artificial. Some translators use equivalent dialects in the target language; others recreate dialectal flavor through idiomatic expressions or nonstandard grammar. For example, translating Yorkshire English into Uzbek may involve using colloquial Uzbek vocabulary or sentence patterns typical of rural speech. As Baker (2011) points out, dialects often carry “social and emotional resonance” that standard language cannot reproduce (p. 48, *In Other Words*). However, direct substitution is rarely effective- since dialects function differently in each society. In such cases, translators rely on compensatory strategies: adjusting tone, register, and cultural markers to maintain authenticity. Dialects in literature, therefore, are not only linguistic variants but also social symbols that require sociolinguistic empathy from the translator.

Language reflects the social distance between speakers. In many languages, such as Japanese, French, or Korean, politeness and speech level are grammatically encoded. Translating these distinctions poses major difficulties because English, for example, expresses politeness more pragmatically than morphologically. Nida (1964) emphasized that achieving dynamic equivalence requires reproducing the same communicative effect in the target culture, even if the form changes (p. 91, *Toward a Science of Translating*). Translators must analyze not only what is said but who says it, to whom, and under what circumstances. For instance, the English informal “Hey, come here!” might be translated into Uzbek as “Hoy, bu

yoqqa kel!” for friendly tone, but as “Iltimos, bu yoqqa keling,” in formal interaction. The choice reflects sociolinguistic competence. As Hatim and Mason (1997) assert, “register is not a stylistic ornament but a reflection of social relationships” (p. 122, *The Translator as Communicator*). Thus, mastering variation in formality is essential to preserve interpersonal meaning.

In multilingual communities, speakers naturally shift between languages to mark identity or emotional closeness. Translating such code-switching raises questions about authenticity and readability. Should the translator preserve the original mix or normalize it into one language? Bassnett (2002) argues that partial retention of code-switching “signals cultural hybridity and social belonging” (p. 57, *Translation Studies*). For example, in an Uzbek novel where characters switch between Uzbek and Russian, retaining some Russian expressions may enrich the cultural context rather than confuse readers. Similarly, in English-Spanish bilingual texts like those by Sandra Cisneros, code-switching reflects identity negotiation. Translators working with such material must decide which words carry symbolic meaning. As House (2015) notes, translation is a “negotiation of identities” rather than a mere transfer (p. 33, *Translation Quality Assessment*). Hence, translators must understand multilingual practices as cultural strategies, not as linguistic obstacles.

Culture is inseparable from language because it determines how people perceive, categorize, and express reality. Cultural linguistics, as a growing discipline, explores how cultural conceptualizations are embedded in language and how these affect translation. Translators constantly face the dilemma of domestication versus foreignization- whether to adapt the text to the target culture’s norms or retain the foreign flavor. Venuti (1995) describes this as a moral and political choice, since “domestication makes the foreign familiar, while foreignization preserves difference” (p. 20, *The Translator’s Invisibility*).

For instance, idiomatic and metaphorical expressions often contain culture-specific images. Translating “It’s raining cats and dogs” literally into Uzbek would sound absurd, but replacing it with “Yomg‘ir tinmay quyayapti” preserves the intensity of the meaning. The translator’s task is not simply lexical substitution but the recreation of shared cultural imagery. Similarly, addressing systems vary widely across languages. In Uzbek, terms like “aka”, “opa”, or “ustoz” carry deep social respect, while English equivalents (“sir,” “teacher”) may sound more formal than affectionate. Recognizing such nuances allows translators to maintain social relationships encoded in the text.

Sociolinguistics and cultural linguistics together reveal that translation is not a mere linguistic exercise but a deeply social and cultural phenomenon. Every act of translation involves mediating between distinct systems of values, beliefs, and communication styles. A skilled translator must therefore balance linguistic accuracy with cultural sensitivity. Dialectal representation, variation in formality, code-switching, and cultural conceptualizations all serve as windows into the speaker’s identity and worldview. When these are ignored, the translated text loses its soul- it becomes grammatically correct but socially empty. However, when translators approach their work as cross-cultural mediators, they bring life to their translations, enabling readers to experience the richness of another culture through language.

Thus, the translator’s mission extends beyond linguistic fidelity- it encompasses empathy, creativity, and intercultural competence. By integrating sociolinguistic and cultural insights, translators preserve not only meaning but also humanity itself across linguistic borders.

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THE ROLE OF GRAMMAR AND SYNTAX IN ACHIEVING TRANSLATION ACCURACY

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Abstract. This article explores the role of grammar and syntax in translation, with a particular focus on syntactic structures, word order, tense, aspect, and grammatical categories. The accuracy of translation is closely linked to how these elements are preserved or adapted across languages. Syntactic mismatches often lead to shifts in meaning, while differences in word order may influence clarity and style. Furthermore, translating tense and aspect poses significant challenges due to cross-linguistic variation in expressing time and temporality. Finally, the problem of grammatical equivalence is discussed, as categories such as gender, case, or definiteness may not always align between source and target languages. By addressing these issues, the study highlights how grammatical and syntactic awareness contributes to translation accuracy and communicative effectiveness.

Keywords: Grammar, syntax, word order, tense, aspect, grammatical categories, equivalence, translation accuracy.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль грамматики и синтаксиса в переводе, с особым акцентом на синтаксические структуры, порядок слов, время, вид и грамматические категории. Точность перевода тесно связана с тем, как эти элементы сохраняются или адаптируются в разных языках. Синтаксические несоответствия часто приводят к изменению смысла, а различия в порядке слов могут влиять на ясность и стиль. Более того, перевод времени и вида представляет значительные трудности из-за межъязыковых различий в выражении времени и темпоральности. Наконец, обсуждается проблема грамматической эквивалентности, поскольку такие категории, как род, падеж или определённость, могут не всегда совпадать в исходном и целевом языках. Рассматривая эти вопросы, исследование показывает, как грамматическая и синтаксическая осведомленность способствует точности перевода и коммуникативной эффективности.

Ключевые слова: Грамматика, синтаксис, порядок слов, время, вид, грамматические категории, эквивалентность, точность перевода.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola tarjimada grammatika va sintaksisning o‘rnini o‘rganadi. Asosan sintaktik tuzilmalar, so‘z tartibi, zamon va aspekt, hamda grammatik kategoriyalarga e‘tibor qaratiladi. Tarjimaning aniqligi ushbu elementlarning tillararo qanday saqlanishi yoki moslashtirilishiga bevosita bog‘liqdir. Sintaktik nomuvofiqliklar ko‘pincha ma’no siljishiga olib keladi, so‘z tartibidagi farqlar esa matnning aniqligi va uslubiga ta’sir qiladi. Shuningdek, zamon va aspektni tarjima qilish katta qiyinchilik tug‘diradi, chunki vaqt va zamonaviylikni ifodalash tillar o‘rtasida turlicha amalga oshiriladi. Nihoyat, grammatik ekvivalentlik muammosi ham muhokama qilinadi, chunki jins, kelishik yoki aniqlik kabi kategoriyalar har doim ham manba va maqsad tilida mos kelavermaydi. Ushbu masalalarni yoritish orqali

maqola grammatik va sintaktik xabardorlikning tarjima aniqligi va samaradorligiga qo‘shadigan hissasini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Grammatika, sintaksis, so‘z tartibi, zamon, aspekt, grammatik kategoriyalar, ekvivalentlik, tarjima aniqligi.

Grammar and syntax play a vital role in translation because they shape how meaning is conveyed between languages. While words carry the basic content, it is grammar and sentence structure that ensure clarity and accuracy. If these elements are ignored, translations may lose coherence or create misunderstandings. Key aspects include syntactic structures, word order, tense and aspect, and grammatical categories. These features differ across languages, which makes finding proper equivalence a complex task. For example, English has a relatively fixed word order, while some other languages are more flexible, leading to challenges in preserving meaning. This article focuses on how grammar and syntax affect translation outcomes and why translators must consider them carefully to achieve both accuracy and naturalness.

Syntactic structures form the framework through which languages organize meaning. They show how words interact and what relationships exist between them. In translation, the challenge lies in the fact that syntactic rules differ from one language to another. English, for example, has a rigid subject–verb–object (SVO) structure, while languages like German or Uzbek may allow greater flexibility. A literal transfer of syntax may cause sentences to sound awkward or even incorrect in the target language. For instance, a translator working from English to Uzbek must often rearrange sentence parts to make the text natural for Uzbek readers. This adaptation is not a betrayal of the original but a necessary step to maintain both accuracy and fluency. Therefore, syntactic structures are not merely formal elements but directly influence the quality of translation. Skilled translators must identify where syntactic shifts are required and apply them carefully, ensuring the final text preserves meaning without sacrificing readability. [Catford, 1965, pp. 73–75].

Word order is a key component of grammar, but it is not universal. In some languages, like English, word order plays a decisive role in showing grammatical relations. “The dog chased the cat” and “The cat chased the dog” differ only in order, yet the meaning completely changes. In contrast, in languages with case endings such as Uzbek or Russian, word order is more flexible because the endings show who does the action. For translators, this difference presents a real challenge. Simply following the word order of the source text may distort meaning or produce unnatural expressions in the target language. Beyond grammar, word order also conveys stylistic emphasis. Writers often move words for focus or rhythm, and translators must reproduce these effects without confusing readers. Thus, dealing with word order requires both linguistic knowledge and creative adaptation. A good translation respects the original meaning while adjusting the order to sound natural in the target language. [Catford, 1965, p. 77]

Tense and aspect are essential grammatical categories that express time and the manner in which an action unfolds. However, these categories vary significantly across languages, creating challenges for translators. For example, English distinguishes clearly between past simple (“She went”) and present perfect (“She has gone”), while many other languages, such as Uzbek, do not have an exact equivalent for the present perfect. This can lead to subtle shifts in meaning if the translator is not attentive. Aspect adds another layer of difficulty. In Slavic languages, verbs often have perfective and imperfective forms, which indicate whether an action is completed or ongoing. English expresses this through auxiliary verbs and continuous forms, but the nuance is not always the same. A translator must carefully choose structures in the target language that preserve both temporal meaning and aspectual nuance. Thus,

translating tense and aspect is not a matter of direct substitution but of finding functional equivalents that communicate the intended time reference and action quality. Misinterpretation in this area can distort the temporal logic of a text, making the translation less reliable. [Hatim & Mason, 1990, p. 76].

Beyond tense and aspect, other grammatical categories such as gender, number, and case also pose challenges for translators. These categories are not universal and often differ across languages. For example, English nouns have no grammatical gender, while languages like French or Russian assign gender to nearly all nouns. A translator working into English must often omit this information, while translating into gendered languages requires decisions that may not be explicit in the source. Number and case also create difficulties. Some languages, such as Arabic, have a dual form in addition to singular and plural, while English lacks it. Similarly, English relies heavily on word order to show grammatical relations, whereas languages like Uzbek use case endings. Translators must bridge these differences by finding structural equivalents that communicate the same function. Equivalence in grammatical categories is rarely absolute; instead, it depends on how effectively meaning can be adapted. The translator's role is to ensure that these grammatical features are interpreted in a way that preserves both the semantic content and stylistic intent of the original text. [Hatim & Mason, 1990, pp. 101–102].

Grammar and syntax are central to the practice of translation because they determine how meaning is structured and communicated. As shown in this discussion, syntactic structures, word order, tense, aspect, and other grammatical categories all create specific challenges that translators must address. These elements are not uniform across languages, and failing to account for them can result in ambiguity, distortion, or loss of nuance. A successful translation is not only faithful to the source text but also natural in the target language. This balance requires translators to go beyond literal word substitution and engage deeply with grammatical systems. By doing so, they preserve both accuracy and readability, ensuring that the translated text reflects the original meaning while fitting seamlessly into the linguistic norms of the target language.

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INTEGRATING SEMANTIC PERSPECTIVES IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: POLYSEMY, METAPHOR, AND CROSS-LINGUISTIC MEANING TRANSFER

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Abstract. This section explores the semantic dimension of translation, focusing on how meaning is preserved, altered, or lost across languages. It analyzes key linguistic challenges such as polysemy, homonymy, and the translation of figurative language, which often lead to semantic ambiguity. The study also examines cultural and contextual influences that cause semantic shifts and lexical gaps, revealing the limits of linguistic equivalence. By investigating how translators deal with meaning at both lexical and conceptual levels, this research highlights the importance of semantic awareness in achieving accurate and natural translations across different languages and cultures.

Keywords: semantics, meaning, translation, polysemy, metaphor, untranslatability, linguistic equivalence

Аннотация. В этом разделе рассматривается семантическое измерение перевода с акцентом на том, как значение сохраняется, изменяется или теряется в разных языках. Анализируются ключевые лингвистические проблемы, такие как полисемия, омонимия и перевод образного языка, которые часто приводят к семантической неоднозначности. В исследовании также рассматриваются культурные и контекстуальные влияния, вызывающие семантические сдвиги и лексические пробелы, выявляя пределы лингвистической эквивалентности. Рассматривая то, как переводчики работают со значением как на лексическом, так и на концептуальном уровне, данное исследование подчёркивает важность семантической осведомлённости для достижения точного и естественного перевода между разными языками и культурами.

Ключевые слова: семантика, значение, перевод, полисемия, метафора, непереводаемость, лингвистическая эквивалентность

Annotatsiya. Ushbu bo‘lim tarjimada semantik jihatlarni o‘rganadi, ya’ni ma’no tillar o‘rtasida qanday saqlanib qolishi, o‘zgarishi yoki yo‘qolishini tahlil qiladi. Unda polisemiya, gomonimiya va obrazli ifodalarni tarjima qilish kabi semantik noaniqliklarga olib keladigan asosiy tilshunoslik muammolari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, madaniy va kontekstual omillar sabab yuzaga keladigan semantik siljishlar hamda leksik bo‘shliqlar tahlil qilinadi. Maqola tarjimonlarning so‘z va tushuncha darajasida ma’noni qanday uzatishini o‘rganib, tarjimada semantik xabardorlikning to‘g‘ri va tabiiy tarjima uchun naqadar muhimligini ta’kidlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: semantika, ma’no, tarjima, polisemiya, metafora, tarjima qilinmaslik, lingvistik ekvivalentlik

Semantics, the study of meaning, lies at the heart of translation. While grammar and syntax structure sentences, semantics determines the sense conveyed by words and expressions. Translators must therefore navigate the complexities of meaning across languages, where even similar words can differ in nuance, connotation, or cultural implication. Translation becomes especially challenging when words have multiple meanings (polysemy), identical forms with different meanings (homonymy), or when figurative language resists literal interpretation. Furthermore, lexical gaps- cases where one language lacks an equivalent term can make perfect translation impossible. This section explores how semantic phenomena such as polysemy, metaphor, and lexical gaps affect translation and how translators can approach these challenges to achieve both accuracy and cultural resonance.

Polysemy refers to a single word having multiple related meanings, while homonymy occurs when two words share the same form but have unrelated meanings. For instance, the English word “bank” can mean a financial institution or the side of a river. Translating such words requires understanding context to choose the correct meaning. Polysemous and homonymous words create ambiguity because the same form may suggest different interpretations in another language. A translator must analyze semantic context and pragmatic

cues to identify intended meaning. As Nida and Taber (2003, p. 56) note, understanding meaning depends on “the total linguistic and situational context,” not isolated words. Failure to interpret this context can result in misleading or absurd translations (Nida & Taber, 2003, p. 58).

Semantic shifts occur when meanings change during translation due to cultural, historical, or contextual differences. Words that seem equivalent may carry distinct emotional or social connotations. For example, the English word “home” implies warmth and belonging, while its literal translation may not evoke the same emotional depth in another culture. Translators must be aware of these shifts to preserve intended tone and implication. As Hatim and Mason (1990, p. 112) explain, translation involves not only linguistic transfer but also “the negotiation of meaning between cultural contexts.” Semantic shifts often demand rephrasing or compensation techniques to maintain communicative equivalence and cultural relevance.

Metaphor, idioms, and figurative expressions enrich a language but complicate translation. Literal rendering often destroys intended imagery or stylistic effect. For instance, translating the English idiom “spill the beans” literally would confuse readers unfamiliar with the expression. Effective translation of figurative language requires identifying the underlying meaning and finding an equivalent expression in the target language. According to Newmark (1988, p. 104), translators should “reproduce the same image in the target language if possible,” but when this is impossible, they must replace it with a culturally appropriate alternative. This balance ensures that the translation remains expressive while preserving cultural meaning (Newmark, 1988, p. 107).

Lexical gaps occur when a word in one language lacks a direct equivalent in another. For example, the German word “Schadenfreude” (pleasure derived from another’s misfortune) has no single-word equivalent in English. Similarly, cultural concepts like the Japanese “wabi-sabi” or Uzbek “or-nomus” often resist direct translation. Such cases illustrate the concept of untranslatability, where meaning is so deeply tied to culture that any translation risks loss of nuance. As Venuti (2017, p. 145) argues, translators must sometimes “foreignize” the text- preserve original cultural elements- to maintain authenticity. Others, however, prefer “domestication,” adapting unfamiliar terms for readability. The translator’s choice depends on the purpose and audience of the translation (Venuti, 2017, pp. 147–148).

The study of semantics in translation reveals the deep complexity of conveying meaning across linguistic and cultural boundaries. Translators are constantly challenged by issues such as polysemy, homonymy, metaphor, and untranslatability - all of which require not only linguistic competence but also cultural sensitivity and contextual understanding. Accurate translation depends on the translator’s ability to interpret meaning beyond words, considering both cognitive and pragmatic dimensions of language use. By applying semantic awareness and analytical precision, translators can bridge gaps between languages and preserve the communicative intent of the original text. Ultimately, the success of translation lies not in literal equivalence but in achieving functional and conceptual correspondence that resonates within the target culture.

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THE ROLE OF GRAMMAR IN LEARNING A LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article discusses the significance of grammar and syntax in the process of language teaching and learning. It highlights how grammar provides the structural foundation of a language, while syntax organizes words into meaningful sentences. The paper reviews different methods of teaching grammar and syntax, such as contextual learning, task-based learning, and communicative approaches. It also examines the common challenges faced by teachers and learners when dealing with grammatical and syntactic structures. The author emphasizes that grammar should not be taught as a set of isolated rules but should be integrated into real communication. The conclusion suggests that combining accuracy and fluency in grammar teaching helps learners use the language naturally and effectively.

Keywords: grammar, syntax, language teaching, communication, pedagogy.

Introduction. When we learn or teach a new language, grammar and syntax are two things we always deal with, even if we don't notice it at first. Grammar shows us how to use words correctly, while syntax helps us put them in the right order to make clear and meaningful sentences. In language teaching, these two parts are very important because they help learners understand how the language really works. In the past, teachers often focused only on memorizing grammar rules. But today, teaching is more about using grammar in real communication -through speaking, writing, and understanding. Good teachers now try to make grammar something practical and connected to everyday use. Grammar is like the backbone of any language. Without it, communication becomes confusing. When students understand grammar, they can express themselves more clearly and confidently:

- Good grammar teaching helps students to:
- Build correct sentences naturally.
- Avoid basic mistakes in writing and speaking.
- Understand how meaning changes when grammar changes.

However, grammar lessons should not only be about rules and drills. Students learn better when grammar is connected to real situations - stories, dialogues, and activities. For example, instead of just teaching the past tense as "-ed" endings, teachers can let students tell short stories about what they did yesterday. This makes grammar more alive and memorable.

Understanding Syntax. Syntax is about how words are arranged to form a sentence. Every language has its own order. For example, in English we usually say "She reads a book," not "Reads she a book." This shows that syntax gives meaning through structure. For language learners, syntax helps them:

- Build sentences that sound natural.
- Understand long or complex sentences while reading.
- Write better paragraphs and compositions.

Teachers can teach syntax through examples and sentence-building games. When students create their own sentences, they start to "feel" how the language flows. This feeling is more powerful than memorizing rules alone.

How to Teach Grammar and Syntax Effectively. There are many ways to teach grammar and syntax. Each class is different, so teachers often mix several methods. Some of the best ways include:

- Teaching in context: showing grammar through stories, conversations, or real-life examples.
- Discovery learning: letting students find rules by themselves after seeing examples.
- Task-based activities: giving students tasks where grammar is needed to complete them, like planning a trip or writing a dialogue.
- Integration with skills: combining grammar with reading, writing, or speaking lessons so it feels natural.
- When grammar and syntax are part of communication, students see them as useful tools, not just boring rules.

Common Challenges. Many teachers find grammar and syntax hard to teach because:

- Students may lose interest if the lesson feels too technical.
- Some learners mix up rules from their first language.

There isn't always enough time to explain everything in class. To solve this, teachers should use creative activities, visual examples, and group work. Grammar doesn't have to be dry - it can be fun if it connects to real communication.

Grammar and Syntax in Communication. Grammar and syntax are not separate from speaking, reading, writing, or listening. They are part of all language skills:

- In speaking, they help make ideas clear and polite.
- In writing, they create logical and correct sentences.
- In reading, they help understand how meaning is built.
- In listening, they help catch patterns and structures quickly. When grammar and syntax are taught together with these skills, students learn faster and remember longer.

Conclusion. To sum up, grammar and syntax are essential parts of language learning. They help learners speak and write with confidence and accuracy. The goal is not only to know the rules but to use them naturally. Teachers should make grammar and syntax lessons meaningful, interesting, and connected to real communication. When learners understand grammar through practice, they gain real language ability - not just memorized knowledge.

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PHONETICS AND PHONOLOGY IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract: Phonetics and Phonology are two important branches of linguistics. Phonetics studies speech sounds in terms of their formation, physico-acoustic properties, and hearing. Phonology, on the other hand, analyzes the role of sounds in the language system, function and differentiation of meaning. Hence, phonetics illuminates the external and Phonology the internal systematic side of sounds. The role of phonetics and Phonology in Language Teaching is incomparable. These two areas are important in developing students' phonemic hearing, eliminating pronunciation errors, and improving oral speech skills. The purpose of this article is to highlight the role and importance of phonetics and Phonology in Language Teaching, especially in the process of correct pronunciation formation, to explain the relationship of these two areas on a scientific basis.

Keywords: Physico-acoustic, systematic, Greek *phōnētikōs*, wavelength, timbre, spectrograph, oscillograph, rhythm, classification, doctrine elongated, articulatory, juxtaposition, phonemic hearing, pronunciation, techniques, phonetics, dialects, tongue twisters, seashells, participation, articulatory, intonation, interprets, melody, accentuation.

General understanding of phonetics. Phonetics (from Greek *phōnētikós* – “concerning the voice”) is a branch of linguistics that studies speech sounds in terms of their generation, hearing, and physical properties. In linguistics, phonetics deals with the external aspect of the language system, that is, it examines how sounds are articulated, acoustically shaped, and perceived through hearing. Main branches of phonetics: Articulatory phonetics – studies the process of formation of sounds with the help of speech organs (tongue, lip, palate, hoarseness, etc.). Acoustic phonetics – studies the physical properties of sound (vibration frequency, wavelength, strength, timbre). Auditor phonetics – analyzes how the human ear perceives sounds and how they are processed in the brain. Experimental phonetics – examines sounds using special apparatus (spectrograph, oscillograph, etc.). Object of study of phonetics, Speech sounds are vowels and consonants. A syllable is the smallest rhythmic branch of speech. Stress (stress) – stronger pronunciation of a particular syllable. Intonation is the tone, rhythm and melody of a sentence. Pause-interruptions in speech. Functions of phonetics: Classification and interpretation of language sounds. Development of pronunciation standards. Expression of speech sounds in writing (transcription). Determination of the importance of the sound system in language learning and teaching. Importance of phonetics For linguistics – important in the identification of phonemes and phonological system. Language plays a key role in teaching – pronunciation, accentuation and intonation. In technique and technology – speech synthesis and familiar (for example, Google Translate, Voice Assistants) are based on phonetics. In speech therapy and medicine – correction of speech defects, knowledge of phonetics will be needed. Phonetics and Phonology difference: Phonetics – studies the physical and articulatory properties of sounds. Phonology – the function of sounds in the language system and the distinguishing feature of meaning. Concept of phonology: Phonology (from Greek *phōnē* – “sound” + *logos* – “doctrine”) is the branch of linguistics that studies speech sounds in terms of their function in the language system and the point of their role in meaning differentiation. If phonetics studies the physical and articulatory aspects of sounds, phonology analyzes the role and function of sounds in the linguistic system. The main object of phonology: A phoneme is the smallest sense differentiating unit of sound. For example: the phonemes [p] and [b] in *pal* – *bal* differ. Allophone is a variant of phoneme in pronunciation. For example, the phoneme /p/ in English is pronounced like *pin* [p^h] (aspirated) and *spin* [p] (unaspirated). Phonological opposites are pairs such as consonant–consonant, elongated–short vowel, nasal–oral vowels. Phonotactics is how sounds can be combined within a language. For example, in English, the word does

not have /ŋ/ at the beginning, while in Uzbek it comes (ngiz). The main tasks of phonology Identification and classification of the phoneme system of the language. Study of the role of sounds in meaning differentiation. Development of phonological rules and phonotactics. Research of accentuation, intonation and phonological features of the joint system.

Phonetics in Language Teaching. Phonetics occupies a special place in the process of Language Teaching. One of the biggest problems of students studying a foreign language is the question of the formation of correct pronunciation. Following the pronunciation norm, clearly and fluently speaking sounds is based on phonetic knowledge. The teacher will first explain to the students the process of formation of sounds, the participation of articulatory organs and their correct use. Phonetics also develops the skills of hearing and saying speech sounds in students. The exercise of being able to hear sounds clearly, distinguishing them, pronouncing them and repeating them again encourages students to actively participate. Audio materials, speech recordings, sound discrimination exercises are important in this process. Another area of phonetic exercise in Language Teaching is the teaching of stress (stress), intonation, and rhythm. Each language has its own accent rules and tone system. For example, in English, stress does not fall on the last syllable as in Uzbek, but often comes on the first or second syllable (TABLE, PREtty). When students learn to say a sentence with intonation, their speech sounds more natural and fluent. In phonetics classes, it is important to use minimal Pairs to effectively organize training. For example, in English, one can show that a single sound difference changes the whole meaning of a word through pairs such as ship – sheep, bat – pat, pen – pan. In addition, listening repetition exercises (listening and repeating) also serve as a key tool in improving pronunciation and developing phonemic hearing in students.

Phonology in Language Teaching. Phonology plays an important role in explaining the function of sounds in the language system to students during Language Teaching. The phonological system of each language is unique, and if the reader does not master it thoroughly, he may have difficulty in pronunciation and understanding speech. Therefore, teaching phonological rules is one of the important conditions for effective teaching of a foreign language. One practical aspect of phonology is the explanation of phonological rules. For example, in English, the plural suffix-s of nouns is pronounced in three different ways: /s/ (cats), /z/ (dogs), /ɪz/ (buses). When a teacher interprets these rules to students from a phonological point of view, they learn to correctly apply words not only in writing, but also in pronunciation. Phonology also helps explain phonotactic rules. Each language has its own limitations in the juxtaposition of sounds. For example, English does not have the vowel /ŋ/ at the beginning of a word, while in Uzbek it may come (ngiz). Knowing such differences allows the reader to consciously master the language. Another function of phonological training is the development of phonemic hearing in students. The reader should be able to hear certain sounds and distinguish them from other sounds. For example, in English, distinguishing between bit and beat, fan and van in pronunciation and hearing indicates the formation of phonemic hearing. As this skill develops, students feel much relief in listening and understanding speech and correcting their pronunciation.

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ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА РУБАЙЯТОВ ОМАРА ХАЙЯМА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается вопрос влияния лексико-семантической переводческой трансформации на перевод рубаийят Хайяма. Автор пытается проанализировать перевод четверостишия, сопоставляя его с другими переводами, исследовать характерные особенности и ценность переводов. Автор исследовал отличия переводов Фитцджеральда от других переводов, определил его достоинства и недостатки. Автором изучена проблема использования приемов лексической трансформации на примере переводов четверостиший. **Ключевые слова:** перевод поэтических текстов, четверостишие, Омар Хайям, Фицджеральд, сопоставительный анализ переводов, лексико-семантические трансформации.

Abstract. The article examines the influence of lexico-semantic translation transformations on the translation of Khayyam's *Rubaiyat*. The author attempts to analyze the translation of a quatrain by comparing it with other versions, exploring their distinctive features and value. The study investigates the differences between FitzGerald's translation and other renderings, identifying its strengths and weaknesses. The issue of employing lexical transformation techniques is analyzed through examples from the translations of the quatrains.

Keywords: *translation of poetic texts, quatrain, Omar Khayyam, FitzGerald, comparative analysis of translations, lexico-semantic transformations.*

Несомненно, что перевод поэзии является намного сложнее перевода других художественных жанров, поскольку поэзия обладает особенностями метрики, рифмы, редифа, философии смысла, художественных средств выражения и эстетического влияния. Указанные особенности весьма трудно включить в текст перевода, это требует обширных знаний, достаточного опыта, а также большого таланта в передаче смыслов и поэтического мастерства.

В процессе использования лексических трансформаций наиболее часто используемыми методами являются методы конкретизации, генерализации, модуляции, транскрипции и транслитерации. Однако следует отметить, что помимо метода лексических трансформаций широко используются также метод вольного перевода и дословный перевод.

Сущность использования стилистических трансформаций выражается в том, что переводчик в большинстве случаев меняет единицы языка перевода в стилистическом отношении и в плане смысловых оттенков.

Л.К. Латышев подчеркивает, что особенности использования средств выражения языка оригинала и использования особенностей контекста основываются на переводческих трансформациях [5, С. 125].

По мнению Г.М. Стрелковского, сведения текста оригинала представляются в виде конкретного речевого текста, и коммуникативные отношения считаются более необходимыми. Главное требование к точному функциональному переводу - это не соответствие единиц языка оригинала и перевода, а функциональная идентичность речи и эквивалентность текстов [5, С. 23].

Необходимо отметить, что в современный период изучение и исследование лексических трансформаций получило широкое распространение. Однако специфика перевода произведений на таджикский и английский языки в части использования переводческих трансформаций остается малоизученной областью лингвистики.

Ниже мы рассмотрим использование лексических трансформаций в переводах рубайатов Омара Хайяма.

Т а б л и ц а 1

Исходный текст	Перевод I	Перевод II	Тарчумаи III
<p><i>Ҳар сабза, ки дар каноре ҷӯе рустааст, Ғӯи, зи лаби ғаришмахӯе рустааст. Ҳон, бар сари сабза по ба хорӣ наниҳӣ, К-он сабза ба хоки лоларӯе рустааст [10, С. 128].</i></p>	<p><i>Every green grass that grown along the fringes of a brook, so to say, has sprung from the lips of one angelic temper. Be careful not to set your foot upon the grass in contempt, for that grass has sprung from the dust of one of tulip-tinted cheeks [14, С. 14].</i></p>	<p><i>And this delightful Herb whose tender Green, Fledges the River's Lip on which we lean Ah, lean upon it lightly! for who knows. From what once lovely Lip it springs unseen! [12, С. 38]</i></p>	<p><i>Yon turf, fringing the margent of the stream, As down upon a cherub's lip might seem, Or growth from dust of buried tulip cheeks; Tread not that turf with scorn, or light esteem! [10, С. 128].</i></p>

В приведенной таблице рассмотрены три примера перевода. В переводе I фраза «*ҳар сабза*» - “*Every green grass*” /всякая трава» переводится методом кальки, за которой следуют слова “*канори ҷӯе*” - “*fringes of a brook*” «у ручья» и “*лаби ғаришмахӯе*” - “*lips of one angelic temper*” «уста ангельского нрава». Однако переводы II и III показывают, что это было достигнуто посредством описательного метода, дополнительных трансформаций и компенсации смысла и сокращения. Например, словосочетание “*ҳар сабза*” - “*this delightful Herb whose tender Green*” - «эта вкусная трава, у которой нежная зелень» и словосочетание “*лаби ғаришмахӯе*” - “*River's Lip*” переведено методом компенсации путем добавления “*on which we lean*” - «на что мы опираемся».

В переводе III словосочетание “*Ҳар сабза*” - “*Yon turf*” (каждая травинка) и “*канори ҷӯе*” - “*fringing the margent of the stream*” переведено также методом кальки. Но словосочетание “*лаби ғаришмахӯе*” - “*a cherub's lip*” (губы ангелоподобной) переведено дословно.

Во втором бейте словосочетание “*бар сари сабза по ба хорӣ наниҳӣ*” - “*Be careful not to set your foot upon the grass*” - не ступай сильно по траве передано методом кальки, и находится в состоянии семантической асимметрии.

Также словосочетание “*хоки лоларӯе*” - “*the dust of one of tulip-tinted cheeks*” - «земля с цветом тюльпанового лика» передано как дословно, так и описательным методом. Но в переводе II словосочетание «*lean upon it lightly! for who knows*» - ступай тихонько, ведь никто не знает, переведено полностью и семантически равнозначно. Также словосочетание «*From what once lovely Lip*» было передано посредством семантической компенсации.

В переводе строки «*К-он сабза ба хоки лоларӯе рустааст*» - “*growth from dust of buried tulip cheeks*” - «Ведь этот росток вырос на земле с цветом тюльпанового лика» использован метод компенсации содержания. Из исследования указанного рубаи следует, что перевод I и II относительно лучше, чем перевод III, с точки зрения

семантики и соблюдения поэтических норм. Поскольку переводы I и II принадлежат Эдварду Фицджеральду, он осуществлял перевод чаще посредством метода вольного перевода.

Т а б л и ц а 2

Исходный текст	Перевод I	Перевод II	Перевод III
<p><i>Ин қофилау умр ачаб мегузарад. Дарёб даме, ки бо тараб мегузарад. Соқӣ, гами фардои қиёмат чӣ хӯрӣ?</i></p> <p><i>Пеш ор ниёларо, ки шаб мегузарад.</i></p> <p>[10, С. 170].</p>	<p><i>This caravan of life is in a strange way passing.</i></p> <p><i>Take advantage for a while, for it is merrily passing.</i></p> <p><i>O, Saki, why do you grieve for tomorrow`s rivals? Bring forth the cup, for the night is passing</i> [14, С. 13].</p>	<p><i>Ah, fill the Cup: - what boots it to repeat</i></p> <p><i>How Time is slipping underneath our Feet:</i></p> <p><i>Unborn tomorrow and dead yesterday,</i></p> <p><i>Why fret about them if to-day be sweet!</i> [12, С. 60]</p>	<p><i>Life`s caravan is hastening on its way:</i></p> <p><i>Brood not on troubles of the coming day,</i></p> <p><i>But fill the wine cup, ere sweet night be gone,</i></p> <p><i>And snatch a pleasant moment while you may</i> [10, С. 170].</p>

В переводе I словосочетания “*қофилау умр*” - “*caravan of life*” - «караван жизни» - и “*ачаб мегузарад*” - “*is in a strange way passing*” - «чудесно проходящий» переданы дословно, и лексические значения единиц полностью совпали.

Наряду с этим, перевод III также выполняется буквально, но глагол *hastening* (спешить) метафорически с глаголом «пройти» совместим лишь иносказательно.

В строке “*Ин қофилау умр ачаб мегузарад*” - *How Time is slipping underneath our Feet* (Как время ускользает из-под наших ног) Фицджеральд сравнивает словосочетание «*қофилау умр*» со словом «время».

Кроме того, словосочетание «*ачаб мегузарад*» - “*is slipping underneath our Feet*” - «ускользает из-под наших ног» было интерпретировано в поэтической форме, с использованием художественных образов, методом семантического улучшения, смысловой компенсации и описательного перевода.

В то же время словосочетание “*Дарёб даме*” - “*Take advantage for a while*” - «воспользуйся временем» в переводе I передано посредством семантической компенсации и семантического улучшения. Продолжение строки “*бо тараб мегузарад*” - “*it is merrily passing*” - «весело проходит» переведено буквально.

В переводе III эта строка передано следующим образом:

And snatch a pleasant moment while you may.

И воспользуйся временем, пока можешь.

Стремись за счастьем, пока можешь.

Из стилистики перевода явствует, что переводчик использовал методы семантического улучшения, компенсации смысла и радикального изменения, которое называется вольным переводом.

Следует отметить, что автор III перевода в переводе второй строки также применил метод перемещения.

В переводе II также осуществлен перевод посредством поэтической стилизации:

Why fret about them if to-day be sweet!

Чаро гами онро хӯрам, ҳол он ки имрӯз хуш мегузарад.

Зачем беспокоиться об этом, коли сегодня все хорошо.

В вышеприведенном примере передача второй и третьей строки смешалась, и переводчик во избежание повтора, словосочетание «*фардоу қиёмат*» передал «*Unborn to-morrow and dead yesterday*» следующим образом: (*Касе, ки фардо ба дунё наояд, пас вай дирӯз аз олам гузаштааст / Тот, кто не родится завтра, значит вчера он скончался*).

В приведенном выше переводе также использованы методы компенсации содержания, радикального изменения и семантического улучшения.

Третья строка интерпретируется, также как I перевод, буквально: *гами фардоу қиёмат чӣ хӯрӣ - why do you grieve for tomorrow's rivals? Зачем горевать о Судном дне - зачем скорбеть о завтрашних соперниках?*

Указанная строка переведена в вопросительном тоне, и тон предложения изменился.

Brood not on troubles of the coming day.

Аз гуссаҳои рӯзи оянда андӯҳгин машав.

Не думай о бедах завтрашнего дня.

Приведенная строка также передана методом конкретизации.

Фицджеральд (в переводе II) перевел третью строку “*Unborn to-morrow and dead yesterday. Why fret about them*” «*Завтра не родится и умер вчера. Зачем волноваться о них*», и воспользовался методом компенсации смысла и семантического улучшения.

Кроме того, словосочетания «*Пеш оп ниёларо*» и «*шаб мегузарад*» в переводе I переведены методом кальки:

Пеш оп ниёларо, ки шаб мегузарад.

Bring forth the cup, the night is passing.

Принеси чашу, ведь ночь проходит.

Однако в III переводе указанная строка передана посредством метода компенсации и семантического улучшения:

Пеш оп ниёларо, ки шаб мегузарад.

Fill the wine cup, ere sweet night be gone.

Наполни чашу вином, пока не прошла сладкая ночь.

В переводе II наблюдается использование методов компенсации смысла, изменения содержания и стилистики:

Пеш оп ниёларо, ки шаб мегузарад.

Ah, fill the Cup: - what boots it to repeat.

Ах, наполни кубок (вином): ведь ничто не заставит ее (ночь) вернуться вновь.

Переводчик передал вторую часть стиха с ясным и лаконичным смыслом. Как наблюдается, в II и III переводах чаще используются различные лексические трансформации.

Было установлено, что в процессе перевода использовались разные методы и подходы. Например, в переводах I и II Фицджеральд в основном использовал переводческие трансформации и вольный перевод.

В то же время переводчики использовали методы грамматической замены и лексической трансформации (компенсация содержания, изменение значения и семантическое улучшение значения). Кроме того, метод кальки также используется в переводах I и III, поскольку переводчики ограничены лексическим значением единиц.

Также в III переводе присутствуют признаки вольного перевода в соответствии с правилами метрической системы таджикско-персидского стихосложения, а переводчик в основном использовал методы идентификации, обобщения, семантического

улучшения, компенсации содержания, изменения смысла, стилистических и семантических трансформаций.

Однако следует отметить, что некоторые противоречивые случаи наблюдались в результате влияния безэквивалентной лексики.

Переводы Эдварда Фицджеральда, на наш взгляд, благодаря их особому стилю и глубокому содержанию, имеют преимущество, поскольку его интерпретация соответствует содержанию духовного мира Омара Хайяма, а его книга произведение знакомит читателя с истинной сутью и посылами великого поэта.

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О‘ЗBEK VA TURK TILLARIDAGI ZONIM KOMPONENTLI FRAZEMALAR TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada frazemalar va ularning mazmuni, o‘zbek va turk tillaridagi frazemalarning faol yadro komponentiga ko‘ra guruhlanishi, frazemalarda har bir xalqning urf-odati, qadriyati, an‘analari va dunyoqarashlari aks etishi, ularning shakllanishida geografik joylashuvlarning namoyon bo‘lishi haqida qisqacha to‘xtalib o‘tiladi. Maqolada turli komponentli frazemalarni tahlil qilgan holda, o‘zbek va turk tillaridagi zoonim komponentli frazemalar alohida tadqiq etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: frazema, ibora, faol yadro, zoonim komponent, o‘zbek tili frazemalari, turk tili frazemalari.

Ma‘lum bir xalqning urf-odatlari, qadriyatlari, dunyoqarashi, fikrlash doirasi va yashash sharoitlari haqida ma‘lumot beruvchi leksik birliklar tarkibiga frazemalar taalluqlidir. Frazemalar so‘z birikmasi va gap shakliga ega bo‘lgan, ma‘nosi bir so‘zni taqazo qiladigan semantik birliklardir. Frazemalarni keng va tor ma‘noda tushunish farqlanadi. Keng

ma'nodagi frazeologik birliklar tarkibiga frazema bilan birgalikda maqol, matal, hikmatli so'zlar ham kiritiladi. Tor ma'noda esa faqat frazemalar tushuniladi.

Frazemalarni komponentlarga ajratishda ot, fe'l komponentli frazemalar kabi turlarga ajratishadi. Ammo o'zbek va turk tillaridagi frazemalarni ot tarkibli, fe'l tarkibli tarzida guruhlash nisbiydir. Chunki frazeologik birliklarning har biri tarkibida ot leksema ishtirok etadi. Shu bois o'zbek va turk tillaridagi frazemalar faol yadro komponentiga ko'ra quyidagicha guruhlandi:

1. Soma tarkibli frazemalar;
2. Zoonim tarkibli frazemalar;
3. Gastronomik tarkibli frazemalar;
4. Kiyim-kechak tarkibli frazemalar.

Soma tarkibli frazemalar dunyo tillarida eng katta guruhni o'z ichiga oluvchi lug'aviy birliklar hisoblanadi. So'z birikmasi ko'rinishidagi frazemalar soma komponentining turli turkumdagi so'zlar bilan birikuvidan hosil bo'lgan. Soma komponentning aksariyat o'rinda fe'l leksema bilan birikishdan hosil bo'lishi kuzatiladi.

Sh.Usmonova o'z tadqiqotida o'zbek va turk tillaridagi somatik frazeologizmlarni aniq raqamlar orqali beradiki, unga ko'ra o'zbek tilida 1800 ta somatik ibora bo'lsa, turk tilida 1700 ta somatik ibora borligini aytib o'tgan. Va bu frazeologizmlarni ifodalashda o'zbek tilida 97 ta soma, turk tilida 71 ta soma qatnashganligini ta'kidlaydi [4, 13].

Soma yadroli frazemalarning o'zbek tilida ham, turk tilida ham nisbatan ko'p miqdorni tashkil etishi aniqlandi.

O'zbek tilida bo'lgani kabi turk tili ham iboralarga boy til hisoblanadi va badiiy uslub bilan birga og'zaki so'zlashuv uslubida ham iboralardan keng foydalaniladi.

O'zbek va turk tillarida taom va kiyim-kechak nomlari ishtirok etgan frazemalar ham talaygina. Ayrim frazemalarda bu birliklar har ikki tilda barqaror birikmalar semantikasining farqli ifodalanishini namoyon etadi.

Xamirdan qil sug'urganday [3, 380] / *çorap söküğü gibi* [1, 575]. O'zbek tilida xamirdan qil sug'urganday frazemasini "osonlik bilan, hech qanday qiyinchiliksiz" degan ma'nolarni ifodalaydi: *Achchiq sho'rva ichib, ko'rpaga o'ralib yotsangiz, chunonam bir terlaysizki, dardingiz xamirdan qil sug'urganday chiqib ketadi*. S.Ahmad. Hukm.

Turk tilida ayni ma'nolarni ifodalash uchun *Çorap söküğü gibi gitmek* "Paypoq choki kabi ketmoq" / *Tereyağından kıl çeker gibi* "Sariyog'dan qil sug'urgan kabi" frazemalari ishlatiladi. *Başlayan bir işten sonra ona ve birbirine bağlı birçok iş arka arkaya ve kolaylıkla sürüp gitmek / Kimseye zarar vermeden, çok kolaylıkla*. "Boshlangan bir ishdan so'ng unga bog'liq ishlar birin-sirin va oson bitadi / Hech kimga zarar yetkazmasdan, oson, silliq".

O'zbek tilida *bir kun tuz ichgan joyingga qirq kun salom ber* maqoli mavjud. Ya'ni, kichik bo'lsa ham yaxshilik ko'rgan insonni, uning qilgan yaxshiligini hech qachon unutmaslik kerak. Shu mazmuni ifodalash uchun *non-tuz haqqi* frazemasini qo'llaymiz. Qaysi millat vakili bo'lmasin insoniylik yuzasidan yaxshilikni hech qachon unutmaydilar. O'zbek va turk xalqi ham non, tuz haqqini unutmaydigan millat hisoblanishadi.

Turk tilida *tuz ekmek hakkı* frazemasini mavjud. Sofrasında yemek yediği ve iyiliklerini gördüğü kimsenin kendisi üzerinde bulunduğu kabul edilen hak, duygusal borç. Shu bilan birga turk xalqi qahvalari bilan ham mashhurdir. Mehmonning hurmati sifatida, albatta, qahva ikrom etiladi. Turk tilida İyilik küçük de olsa unutulmaz (yaxshilik kichik bo'lsa ham unutilmaydi) mazmuni ifodalovchi *bir fincan kahvenin kirk yıl hatırı vardır* [5, 16] iborasi ham qo'llaniladi (bir finjon qahvaning qirq yil hurmati bor).

Kiyim kechak nomi bilan bog'liq *to'nini teskari kiyib olmoq / Pabucu ters giydirmek* frazemalari mavjud.

O'zbek tilida *to'n(i)ni teskari kiyib olmoq* frazemasi "o'chakishgan holda qaysarlik qilmoq" ma'nosini bildiradi: *Bir majlisda Bekniyoz uni: "Zanglab qolyapsiz, Boqijon aka", – deb tanqid qildi. Shu bo'ldi-yu, Boqijon aka to'nini teskari kiyib oldi.* Varianti: *to'n(i)ni ters kiyib olmoq* (kam ishlatiladi). Turk tilida *Pabucu ters giydirmek* "oyoq kiyimini ters kiydirmoq" /*külahı ters giydirmek* "bosh kiyimni teskari kiydirmoq" frazemalari bilan ifodalanadi. *Eksik olma çocuğum... Bilirim ama, onlar şeytana külahını ters giydirirler* [6, 99]. O'zbek madaniyatida g'azablanish, jahlning chiqishi ust kiyim (*to'n*) orqali aks ettirilgan bo'lsa, turk madaniyatida bosh kiyim (*külah*) va oyoq (*pabucu*) kiyimi yordamida aks ettiriladi.

Do'ppi(si)ni osmonga otmoq kim [o'zining] juda xursand bo'lmoq, quvonmoq. Varianti: *do'ppi(si)ni osmonga irg'itmoq; do'ppi(si)ni osmonga tashlamoq. Sizni qarang, men "to'rt" olsam, do'ppimni osmonga otgan bo'lardim!* O.Yoqubov. Muqaddas.

Külahını (fesini) havaya atmak. Çok sevinmek. Barcha kiyim-kechaklarga hurmat ko'rsatganimiz holda, bosh kiyim oyoq ostida turmaslik kerakligi doimo kattalar tomonidan eslatib turiladi. Har ikkala tilda ham xursandchilik o'zi yuqorida bo'lgan bosh kiyimning yana ham yuqoriga ko'tarilishi bilan izohlangan.

Hayvon va hayvon ta'na a'zolari nomlari bilan ifodalanadigan frazemalarni zoonim komponentli frazemalar tarkibida o'rganamiz. "Zoonim komponentli matnlarni o'rganish turli xalqlar madaniy xususiyatlari bilan tanishish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, bu jarayon hozirda mavud bo'lmagan hayvonlar haqida ma'lumotga ega bo'lish, madaniyatlar mushtarakligi yoki farqli jihatlarini aniqlash imkoniyatini ham yaratadi" [7, 12]. Chuqur tadqiq qilinadigan bo'lsa, zoonim tarkibli frazemalarni ham mayda guruhlarga bo'lib o'rganish mumkin. Masalan, yirtqich hayvonlar, uy hayvonlari, sudralib yuruvchilar, qushlar, baliqlar va hokazo. Bunday frazemalar o'zbek tilida ham turk tilida ham salmoqli miqdorni egallaydi. Har ikkala tilda ham zoonim yadroli frazemalar insonlarning fe'l-atvori, xatti-harakati, dunyoqarashlarini ifodalashga xizmat qiladi.

Oralar(i)dan ola mushuk o'tdi. Varianti: *oralari(i)dan qora mushuk o'tdi; o'rtalar(i)dan ola mushuk o'tdi.* Sinonimi: *oraga sovuqchilik tushdi; oraga sovuqchilik tushirmoq; oralar(i)ga sovuqchilik solmoq.* Kimlarning o'zaro normal munosabati yomonlashdi.

Aralarından kara kedi geçmek (aralarına kara kedi girmek) iki dostun arasına soğukluk girmek; iki dost birbirine gücenmek, krş. "Araya söğukluk girmek". Iboralardan guvohi bo'lyapmizki, har ikki xalq tushunchasida mushuk orani buzuvchi, xayrsiz hayvon sifatida tavsiflangan.

"O'zini ko'rmaganga, bilmaganga solmoq" holati har ikki tilda ham bir xil shaklda ifodalanadi: o'zbek tilida: *Tuya ko'rdingmi–yo'q. Iloji bo'lsa, yamatganingizni aytmang, koyib-netib yurmasin tag'in. Tuya ko'rdingmi–yo'q, vassalom.* Oybek. Qutlug' qon.

Turk tilida: *Deve gördün mü! – Neden ölsün (Ne bilirim ne gördüm, deveyi neden ölsün).* *Şu iş üzerine bir şey biliyor musun, tanıklık eder misin diye sorsalar, tanıklık etmek şöyle dursun, böyle bir şeyin söz konusu olmasına karşı bulunduğumu söylerim.–"Deve gördün mü? – Neden ölsün".* "Tuya ko'rding-mi? Bilmayman (nima ko'rganimni bilmayman, tuyani qayerdan bilay?). Shu ish yuzasidan bilasanmi, guvohlik berasanmi, deb so'rasalar, guvohlik berish u yoqda tursin, bu haqida so'z bo'lishiga qarshiman, deymen". Ya'ni har ikki tilda ko'rgan, bilgan ma'lumotini bilmayman, ko'rmadim deyish mumkin, hatto tuya kabi aniq, ravshan ko'rinib tursa ham.

Zoonim yadroli frazemalarda ham o'zbek va turk madaniyatida o'xshashlik ko'p kuzatiladi. Ammo turk xalqining yevropa turmush tarziga yaqin ijtimoiy muhiti, geografik joylashuvi farqli frazemalarning shakllanishiga asos bo'lgan. Masalan, o'zbek tilida *Tuyaning dumi yerga yetganda* frazemasi "hech qachon", mumkin bo'lmagan holatga, voqelikka,

voqea-hodisaga nisbatan ishlatiladi: *Bu suvdan bizga tuyaning dumi yerga yetganda tegadi,– dedi u.* M. Ismoiliy. Farg‘ona tong otguncha.

Turk tilida bu holat *Balık kavağa (kurbağa ağaca) çıkınca* “baliq terakka, qurbaqa daraxtga chiqquncha” frazemasi bilan ifodalanadi. *Baliq* va *qurbaqa* zoonimlarining frazema tarkibida kelishi turk tili egalarining yashash muhitidagi suv havzalarining ko‘pligi bilan bog‘liq. Frazemalardagi *tuya* va *baliq* zoonimlari mantiqiy ziddlikni anglatadi: *tuya* til egasi ongida quruqlik, sahro bilan aloqador manzarani namoyon qilsa, *baliq* suvlik haqidagi tasavvurni uyg‘otadi. *Qurbaqa* zoonimi ham quruqlik, ham *suvlik* bilan bog‘liq manzarani aks ettiradi.

Qanoti ostiga olmoq: kimgadir homiylik qilmoq.

Kanadı altına almak: Korumak, gözetmek, himayesi altına almak.

Ba‘zi frazemalarda hayvon tanasi a‘zolari ko‘chma ma‘nodagi semantikani ifodalashga xizmat qilgan: o‘zbek tilida *tuyog‘(i)ni shiqillatmoq*, “jo‘nab qolmoq”, “ketmoq” ma‘nolarini anglatadi: “*Xo‘p anoyisini topibsanda! Tuyog‘ingni shiqillatib qol!*”- dedi teskari qarab *Ahmad zarda bilan*. Varianti: arava(si)ni tortmoq. Turk tilida bu ma‘no *kuyruğ* “dum” yadroli frazema orqali ifodalanadi: *Çekiver (çek) kuyruğunu. Ondan artık hayır gelmez* (Aşağılanan kişi için). “Dumingni tort. Endi undan yaxshilik kutib bo‘lmaydi (tahqirlash ma‘nosini ifodalaydi). O‘zbek tilida “dumini tug” frazemasi ishlatiladi. *Tuyog, kuyruğ* “dum” insonga nisbatan qo‘llanganda adresantning adresatga nisbatan salbiy munosabatini ifodalaydi.

Arining iniga cho‘p tiqmoq. Varianti: arining inini qo‘zg‘amoq, arining uyasiga tegmoq, arining uyasiga cho‘p tiqmoq. *Kim janjalni qo‘zg‘ab qo‘ymoq*, janjal chiqishiga sabab bo‘lmoq. *Yuqorida o‘tirgan brigadirning gapi arining iniga cho‘p tiqqandek ola-g‘ovurga sabab bo‘ldi*. Mushtum.

Arinin yuvasina (inine) çöp dürtmek. Tehlikeli kishiyci İncitip kışkırtmak: onun kendisine saldırmasına yol açmak

Burgaga achchiq qilib, ko‘rpani kuydirmoq. [Kim] arzimagan narsani deb, jahl ustida nojo‘ya, zararli ishni qilib qo‘ymoq. *O‘z jiyaningiz kuyganidan gapirgandir. Burgaga achchiq qilib, ko‘rpani kuydirish yaxshi emas*.

Bir pire için yorgan yakmak (pire için yorgan yakmak)/ papaza kizip oruç yemek. Önemsiz bir istek uğruna ya da küçük bir zarardan kurtulmak için çok büyük bir zararı göze almak/ bkz. “Gâvura kızıp oruç yemek”. *Avrupa uygarlığını birbirine karıştırmamalıyız. Papaza kızıp oruç bozulmaz. Türklerin yüzü Orta Asya‘dan beri batıya dönüktür*.

Hol(i)ga maymunlar yig‘laydi. Varianti: ahvol(i)ga maymunlar yig‘laydi. *Kimning o‘zi sabab bo‘lgani holda o‘ta og‘ir, achinarli ahvolga tushib qolmoq. Qachongacha men sening eringni poylayman? Kerak bo‘lsa, o‘zing qara!.. Shu ahvoling bo‘lsa, mendan keyin holingga maymunlar yig‘laydi*. A. Qahhor. Sarob.

Hâline köpekler gülüyor: tkz. Çok kötü bir duruma düşenler için kullanılır. Kimningdir juda achinarli holga tushishi o‘zbek millati dunyoqarashida maymunning yig‘lashi, turk tilida esa itning kulishi orqali ifodalangan.

It-mushuk. Dushman. *Shundan so‘ng aholining bir-birlari bilan it-mushuk emas, balki og‘a-ini ekanliklari, qadrdonliklari oydek ravshanlashibdi*. Sh.Bo‘tayev. Haykal

Kedi ile köpek gibi. Birbirleriyle geçinemeyen, anlaşılamayan kimseler için söylenir. Umuman, hayot falsafasida it va mushuk doimo bir-biriga qarshi, biri biriga dushman hisoblanishadi. Bu o‘xshatish insonlar orasidagi kelishmovchilik munosabatiga ham juda mos keladi.

Qush uchsa-qanot(i), odam yursa-oyog‘(i) kuyadi. Aslo chidab bo‘lmaydigan darajada issiq, jazirama. *Qush uchsa-qanoti, odam yursa-oyog‘i kuyadi bizning qirlarda*.

Kuş uçmaz, kervan geçmez. Kimsenin uğramadığı ıssız, sapa, sarp yer. Maarif Müdürü'nün sözleri üzerine şık bir Avrupa köyü gibi görmeye başladığım Zeyniler'e gelince, dağlar arasında kuş uçmaz, kervan geçmez bir yermiş! Bir seneden beri boş olduğu halde en düşkün muallimler bile oraya gitmeye yanaşmıyorlar mış.

O'zbek tilidagi barqaror birikmada frazeologik ma'no qush va odamning harakat imkoniyatlari orqali aks ettirilgan. Turk tilida qush va karvon harakatiga asoslanilgan. O'zbek tilidagi frazemada umumiy tabiiy-ijtimoiy voqelik, turk tilida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, buyuk ipak yo'liga aloqador voqelik aks etgan.

Sichqonning ini ming tanga bo'ldi. Kimga – sichqonning inini ming tanga qilib yubormoq varianti: sichqon ini ming tanga bo'lib ketdi (oz ishlatiladi). Kim kimga qochib qutulgani joy topolmay qolmoq. Shu vaqt deng otam birdan "hay-hay"lab kelib qoldilar-ku; Rahimvoyga sichqonning ini ming tanga bo'ldi. H.Nazir. So'nmas chaqmoqlar.

Siçan deliği bin akçe. Kaçıp saklanacak yer yok.

Ho'kizning qulog'iga tanbur chertmoq. Varianti: qulog'(i)ga tanbur chertmoq kim kimning. Kim gap uqtirishga behuda urinmoq. "Kimga deпти xo'jayin?" - hayron bo'lib so'radi Gulsumbibi. "Ho'kizning qulog'iga tanbur cherttimmi, nodon xotin! - qiziqib ketdi Yormat. - Kimga bo'lar edi, boy otam o'ziga so'rayapti". Oybek. Qutlug' qon

Ayiya kaval çalmak. Anlayışsız bir kimseye bir şey anlatmaya çalışmak. Har ikkala xalq iborasida ham qo'pol, beg'am hayvonlar tanlanganki, gap uqtirganing bilan foydasi yo'q, degan mazmun aglashiladi.

Ikki qardosh til, o'zbek va turk tillaridagi zoonim tarkibli frazemalarni o'rganish jarayonida bir hayvon nomi bilan bog'liq frazemada har ikki tilda bir xil mazmun ifoda etishi bilan birga, bir mazmun turli hayvon nomlari orqali ifoda etishini ham kuzatdik. Bunda so'zlarning denotativ va konnotativ ma'no anglatib kelishini tahlil qilish lozim. O'zbek va turk tillaridagi somatik frazemalarni tadqiq qilgan Sh.Usmonova "Bizningcha, somatik frazeologizmlar keng tushunilishi kerak. Agar hayvon tana a'zolarining nomlari kishilarning xatti-harakatlarini ifodalaydigan iboralarni tashkil toptirsa, u holda bunday iboralarni ham somatik frazeologizmlar tarkibiga kiritish lozim. Jumladan, *dumini tugmoq, dumini tutqizmaslik, dumi xurjunda, tuyog'ini shiqillatmoq, shoxi sindi* singari frazemalar kishilarni tavsiflashga xizmat qilar ekan, ularni somatik frazeologizmlar qatoriga kiritmaslik asossizdir" [4, 11-12-b], -deya ta'kidlaydi. Biz esa, hayvon va hayvon tana a'zolari qismi orqali ifodalangan frazemalarni zoonim tarkibli frazemalarda izohlashni ma'qul deb topdik.

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O'ZBEK VA QOZOQ XALQLARI TILIDA PERAFRAZALAR: LINGVOMADANIY TAHLIL

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek va qozoq tillarida uchraydigan perafrazalarning leksik-semantik, poetik va madaniy jihatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Har ikki xalq tilida perafraza xalq tafakkuri, badiiy didi va dunyoqarashining muhim ifodasi sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: perafraza, o‘zbek tili, qozoq tili, obrazlilik, milliy tafakkur, badiiy ifoda, lingvomadaniyat.

Til – xalq tafakkuri, milliy ruhiyati va madaniyatining eng muhim ko‘zgusidir. O‘zbek va qozoq xalqlari qadimdan bir ildizdan o‘sib chiqqan turkiy elatlar bo‘lib, ularning tillari ham o‘xshash tuzilma va ma’no tizimlariga ega. [1, 26-b]

Tilshunoslikda perafraza (yunoncha periphrasis – “atroflicha ifoda etish”) – biror narsa yoki hodisani to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri nomlamasdan, balki uning belgisi, xususiyati yoki aloqador ma’nosi orqali ifodalashdir. Bu hodisa o‘zbek va qozoq tillarining badiiylilik, obrazlilik va emotsionallik xususiyatlarini yanada kuchaytiradi [1.26-b]. Olimlar – N. Mahmudov (O‘zbek tili) va R. Sizdyqova (Qozoq tili) o‘z tadqiqotlarida perafrazani xalqning milliy tafakkur ifodasi sifatida baholaydilar [2, 52-b].

Perafraza ikki xalq tilida ham so‘z san’atining bir ko‘rinishidir. U fikrni bevosita emas, majoziy yoki tavsifiy yo‘l bilan ifodalaydi. Perafraza yordamida nutq ta’sirchan, badiiy va ifodali tus oladi.

Masalan:

O‘zbek tilida: “Oq oltin” – paxta;

Qozoq tilida: “Қара алтын” – neft;

O‘zbek tilida: “Yurt posboni” – harbiy;

Qozoq tilida: “Отан ұлы” – harbiy;

O‘zbek tilida: “Dil oynasi” – ko‘z;

Qozoq tilida: “Көздің айнасы” – ko‘z [3, 62-b].

Ko‘rinib turibdiki, har ikki tilda perafrazalar majoziy ifoda, ramziy tafakkur, va milliy madaniyatga tayangan holda yuzaga kelgan.

Alisher Navoiy, Abdulla Qodiriy, Erkin Vohidov, Abdulla Oripov kabi adiblar asarlarida perafraza tildagi obrazlilikni kuchaytiruvchi asosiy vosita sifatida qo‘llanilgan. Masalan, Navoiy “quyosh” o‘rniga “osmon chirog‘i”, “ko‘z” o‘rniga “dil oynasi” deb ataydi [7,109-b].

Erkin Vohidov “Sen – mehr daryosi, oq sutli osmonimsan” deb onani samoviy obraz sifatida perafraza qiladi [7,113-b].

Abay Qunanbayev, Jambul Jabayev, Mukagali Makataev kabi shoirlar esa perafrazani xalqona ifoda vositasi sifatida ishlatgan. Masalan, Abayning: “Көзімнің қарасы, көңілімнің санасы” (“Ko‘zimning qorasi, ko‘nglimning ongi”) ifodasi sevimli insonni perafraza yo‘li bilan ta’riflaydi.

Har ikki xalq tilida perafraza milliy qadriyat, urfdan kelib chiqqan tasavvur, tabiat va mehnat hayoti bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir.

O‘zbek tilidagi “oq oltin” (paxta), “non – mo‘jiza”, “ko‘hna shahar” (Buxoro, Samarqand) singari perafrazalar xalqning mehnatsevarlik va qadimiy madaniyatini ifodalasa, Qozoq tilidagi “темір тұлпар” (temir ot – avtomobil), “дала ұлы” (dasht o‘g‘loni – qahramon), “ақ шаңқан арман” (oq orzu – orzular dunyosi) ifodalari dasht hayoti, erkinlik va orzuga sodiqlik ruhini beradi [2, 79-b].

Demak, perafraza – har ikki xalq tafakkuridagi ramziy tilda fikrlash an’anasining badiiy shaklidir.

O‘xshashliklar va farqlar:

– Ikkala tilda ham perafraza so‘z o‘rniga obrazli ifoda yaratadi.

– O‘zbek tilida perafraza ko‘proq madaniy-urban (shahar, hunar, mehnat) tasvirlarda ishlatiladi.

– Har ikki xalqda “oltin”, “yorug‘lik”, “ona”, “yurt” ramzlari ko‘p qo‘llanadi.

– Qozoq tilida esa perafrazalar tabiat, dasht, ot, erk timsollariga tayangan.

– Poetik tilda hissiy ta‘sirni kuchaytiradi.

– O‘zbek adabiyotida arab-fors obrazlari ko‘proq, qozoqda esa xalqona, etnik obrazlar ustun.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak, o‘zbek va qozoq xalqlari tili, adabiyoti va madaniyatida perafrazalar tilning estetik va milliy ifoda qudratini namoyon etadi. Ular har ikki xalqning ramziy tafakkuri, xalqona badiiy fikrlash uslubi va so‘zga hurmatini ko‘rsatadi. Perafraza - bu shunchaki so‘z o‘yinlari emas, balki milliy tafakkur madaniyatining tildagi ifodasidir. Shuning uchun o‘zbek va qozoq tillarida perafrazalarni o‘rganish qiyosiy lingvistika, poetika va madaniyatshunoslik uchun dolzarb ilmiy yo‘nalish hisoblanadi.

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PARAFRAZALARNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola parafrazalar, ularning xususiyatlari, oʻzbek tilida tutgan oʻrni, oʻzbek tilining taraqqiy etishidagi ishtiroki hamda parafrazalarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlarini, olimlarning tadqiqot natijalari va izlanishlar tahlillarini yoritib beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar. Parafraza, omonim parafraza, obrazli, uslubshunoslik, stilistik vosita, lingvokulturologiya, metafora, metonimiya, sinekdoxa.

Til kommunikativ aloqa vositasi sifatida insonlar orasida muloqot jarayonida ishtirok etadi. Shuning bilan birgalikda, madaniyat koʻzgusi hisoblanadi. Unda nafaqat insonni oʻrab turgan borliq, undagi xalqning ijtimoiy hayotini, uning mentalitetini, milliy xarakterini, madaniy anʼanalarini, urf-odat qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi. Til madaniyat xazinasini hisoblanib, leksika, grammatika, iboralar, maqollar, badiiy va ilmiy adabiyotlar orqali boyiydi.

Parafrazalarlar biror narsa hodisaga oʻxshatish orqali tasvirlab ifodalaydi, hamda narsa va hodisaning ikkinchi nomi hisoblanadi. Parafrazalar soʻzning maʼnosini oydinlashtirish, matnni badiiylashtirish, takronni oldini olish kabi uslubiy vazifalarni bajaradi. Oʻzbek tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalarning maʼno-mazmunini ifodalab berish, uning mohiyatini ochib berishi va qaysi uslubda qoʻllanishi uslubshunoslikning asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Parafraza atamasining xorijiy lugʻatlarda turlicha talqini uning farqli va oʻxshash tomonlari xususida bahs yuritilgan. Parafraza aslida “grekcha” soʻz boʻlib (paraphrasis), lingvistikada jumladan, oʻzbek tilshunosligida “tasviriy ifoda” maʼnosida qoʻllanadi. Bu hodisalar hozirgi kunda ham olimlar nazarida chetda qolgan emas. Oʻrganilgan manbalarga xronologik nazar solamiz. Leksikograf olim O.S. Axmanova tahriri ostida nashr qilingan lingvistik qomusiy lugʻatda parafrazaga “biror soʻzni baʼzi predmetlarning soʻzlar orqali oddiy ifodalanishini tasviriy ifoda bilan almashtirishdan iborat boʻlgan koʻchim” deb izoh bergan [1, 312-b] Oʻzbek tilshunosligida koʻchim turi sifatida parafrazani oʻquv qoʻllanmalariga olib kirgan tilshunos olim R.Qoʻngʻurov 1893-yilda nashr etilgan “Oʻzbek tili stilistikasi” qoʻllanmasida: “...kishilarning otlarini yoki boshqa predmetlarning nomini toʻgʻridan toʻgʻri gapirmasdan, ularni turli xil soʻz yoki tasviriy ifodalar vositasida bayon qilish perifraz deyiladi” deb taʼrif bergan [4, 148-b]. Tasviriy ifodalarning parafraza yoki perifraza, parafraz, perifraz deb yuritiladigan nomlari bir xil maʼnoni anglatadi. Bu borada tadqiqot olib borgan tilshunos olimlardan. M.Mirtojiyevning tadqiqotlarida batafsilroq oʻrganilgan.Olimlarning taʼkidlashicha “parafrazalar maʼlum boʻlak yoki koʻchma maʼnoda boʻlib, ular maʼnosi sintezidan tashkil topgan, bir tushunchani bildiruvchi lugʻaviy birliklardir...”

Parafrazalar haqida shu kungacha koʻplab maqolalar va desertatsiyalar ishlangan. Bundan avval parafrazalar maxsus ilmiy tadqiqot obyektini sifatida rejada oʻrganilmagan. Shuningdek, parafrazalar badiiy tasvir vositalaridan biri sifatida ogʻzaki nutqimizda ham yozma nutqimizda ham keng qoʻllanadi. Parafrazalar tilimizning naqadar boyligi hamda taʼsirchan ekanligini ham koʻrsatadi. Ularning shaxs-narsa, buyum, voqea-hodisalarni tasvirlash yoʻli bilan soʻz birikmalari holida ifodalaydigan birikmalarga yoki soʻzga tasviriy ifodalar yoki parafrazalar deb yuritiladi.

Parafraza holida maqom olgan birikmada, garchi semantik qayta boʻlinish kuzatilmaydi” [2,67-b]. Parafrazalar omonim, sinonim hamda metafora, metonimiya va sinekdoxa kabi maʼnoviy shakllari mavjuddir. Omonim parafrazalar nutqimizda bir parafraza

o'rnida qo'llanilsa, unda bular shakldosh parafrazalar. Masalan, Aql gimnastikasi- shahmat, matematika Qora oltin – neft va ko'mir Bahor elchisi- qaldirg'och va deyiladi boychechak kabilar Sinonim parafrazalar esa bir so'zning bir necha tasviriy ifodalari bo'lsa ular ma'nodosh hisoblanadi. Masalan, Televizor-zangori ekran, oynayi jahon Bahor-fasllar kelinchagi, uyg'onish fasli kabi. Metafora asosida ma'no ko'chishida parafrazalar – muayyan hodisa va belgilarning nomini boshqasiga o'zaro tashqi o'xshashlik asosida ko'chirish jarayonidir. Metafora asosida o'xshashlik asosan uning rangi va xususiyatining o'xshashligi yetakchilik qiladi. Misol qilib olsak, qara oltin-neft, oq oltin-paxta, zangori olov-gaz, yashil boylik-ormon kabi. Metonimiya asosida o'xshashlikda bunda biror narsa hodisaning nomi bir narsaga o'xshashlik asosida emas, balki o'zaro bog'liqlik asosida ko'chishidir. Qiyoslaymiz, Alisher Navoiy-g'azal mulkingning sultoni, Abdulla Qodiriy-o'zbek romanchiligining asoschisi yoki paxtakorlar- oq oltin ijodkorlari. Demak, metonimiyadagi predmetlararo bog'liqlik parafrazalarga ham xosdir. Biroq parafrazalardagi o'xshashlik o'zaro bog'liqlik tasviriy - obrazli holatda bo'ladi. Obrazli parafrazalarga biror predmetni unga taalluqli bo'lgan o'xshashlik bilan tasvirlashdir. Bunga misol qilib “oq oltin”, “zangori ekran”, “kumush tola”, “oq chashma”, “zangori olov” kabi.

Sinekdoxa usulida parafrazalarning o'xshashligi, bunda butun orqali qism tasvirlanadi. Professor olim SH.Rahmatullayev sinekdoxani “bir predmetning nomi boshqa bir predmetga qism bilan butun munosabatining aks etishi” dir deb ta'riflaydi. Misol qilib oladigan bo'lsak, peshonasi sho'r, zangori ekran, kumush tola kabi.

Parafrazalar haqida qarashlar qadim zamonlardan mavjud bo'lgan shuningdek, bu haqida qadimgi til va uslubiyat nazariyotchilaridan Aristotel va Kvintilian tomonidan qayd etilganligi, mahalliy va sharqiy slavyan tilshunosligining ham diqqat markazida turganligi manbalarda qayd etilgan [5,143-b].

XX asrning 50-yillarida dunyo tilshunosligida ayniqsa rus tilshunosligida I.Z.Ilina (1954)[15] va V.P.Utkina (1959)[27] olimlar tomonidan lingvistik jarayon sifatida boshqa hodisa yoki vositalar (istiora, metonimiya, sinekdoxa, metafora, majoz, kinoya, sifatlash, kichraytirish, mubolag'a) bilan bog'liq holda tasvirlagan. Jahon tilshunosligida ham atroflicha o'rganilib kelinmoqda. XX asrning 70-yillaridan boshlab o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish bir qadar oshdi. Parafrazalarni lingvistik muammo sifatida birinchilardan bolib V.P.Grigorev tadqiqotlarida so'z-obraz-denotat munosabatlari nuqtai-nazaridan o'rgandi. Olim uni “poetik nutq hosil qilishning eng yorqin qiziqarli va istiqbolli usullaridan biri” deb tavsiflaydi [7,158-b]. Parafrazalar hosil bolishi uchun avvalo, malum bir belgi, narsa va hodisalar asos qilib olinadi. Ular o'ziga tegishli bo'lgan so'z yoki so'zlar bilan nomlanadi va bu belgi va narsalarning so'z bilan munosabati o'rganiladi va lingvistik jarayon sifatida talqin qilinadi. Tilshunoslikda tasviriy ifodalar faqatgina so'zlar bilan shakldoshlik qilingina qolmay ma'lum bir qo'shimchalar orqali ham shakldoshlik hosil qilishi tadqiqotlar natijasida aniqlangan. Bu xususida O'zbek tilshunos olimlaridan Ravshanxoja Rasulov va Ixtiyor Umirovlar parafrazalar borasidagi olib borgan ilmiy tadqiqotlari asosida “O'zbek tili tasviriy ifodalarining izohli lugati” da ta'kidlashicha “Tilshunoslikda shunday so'z yasovchi qo'shimchalar borki, ular orqali ham parafrazalar hosil qilish mumkin. Bunda ma'nodosh qo'shimchalar (sinonimiyasi emas) bir xil yoki har xil o'zaklardan yasalgan so'zlarning parafraza bo'lishi tushunilishi lozim. Bu kabi qo'shimchalardan *-kor*; *-kash*, *-shunos*, *-gir* kabilar parafrazalar yasaydi. Misol uchun: quruvchi o'rnida binokor, pillakor o'rnida zarshunos, yozuvchi o'rnida qalamkash, tilchi o'rnida tilshunos, yaratuvchgi o'rnida binokor kosmanavt o'rnida fazogir kabi ta'sirchanlikni ifoda etuvchi qo'shimchalar mavjudligini asoslab bergan [6.4] O'zbek tilshunosligida parafrazalar ijobiy bo'yoqdorligi yuqori darajadali bilan ajralib turadi. So'zlovchi nutqining ta'sirchanligini oshirib, unga

jozibadorlik baxsh etadi. Shuning uchun ham parafrazalar jamiyatda insonlar orasida ayniqsa, so‘zlashuv uslubida keng qo‘llaniladi. Parafrazalar o‘zbek tilining boyishida asosiy manbalardan biri hisoblanadi. Bizning yurtimizda axloq benihoya serqamrov va qiyosi yoq tushuncha sifatida ardoqlanib kelinadi shu sababli ham So‘zlarning ma‘noli va bejirim usulda qo‘llanilishi va bir so‘z bilan aniq bayon etilish, bizning ham madaniyatimizni ham ma‘naviyatimizni ko‘rsatadi, parafrazalar esa bu borada bizga katta ko‘mak beradi. So‘zlarimizni chiroyli dalillab ifodalab beradi.

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PARAFRAZA VA INSONLARGA QO‘YILGAN LAQABLAR TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kishilarga, ulardagi ijobiy va salbiy holatlariga ishora qiluvchi biror laqab bilan atash mavjudligi to‘g‘risida ham fikr bildirilgan. Shundan so‘ng parafrazalar, ularning stilistik vosita sifatida nutqqa ko‘tarinkilik, obrazlilik baxsh etishi izohlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Parafraza, laqab, obraz, yangidan nomlash, laqab bilan atash, estetik munosabat, parafraza, stilistik vosita, parafrazalarning turlari.

Turkiy xalqlarda voqea-hodisalar va shaxslarni o‘z nomi bilan emas, balki ularning belgi-xususiyatlarini tasvirlash orqali yangidan nomlash hodisasi uchraydi. Shuningdek kishilarga, ulardagi ijobiy va salbiy holatlariga ishora qiluvchi biror laqab bilan atash holati ham mavjud. Bizga ma‘lumki, insonlarga berilgan har qanday tasviriy ifoda yoki laqabda qandaydir estetik munosabat mujassam bo‘ladi. Parafraza (yunoncha “paraphrasis” – tasviriy ifoda, tasvir). Narsa, hodisani o‘z nomi bilan emas, ularni xarakterli belgi-xususiyatlari asosida tasviriy usul bilan ifodalash; shunday ifoda. Masalan: dala malikasi (makkajo‘xori), zangori olov (gaz) kabi [1,80-b] O‘zbek milliy estradasining asoschisi (Botir Zokirov). Parafrazalar nafaqat jozibadorlik, obrazlilik va nutqni boyitish, balki uning mazmunini kuchaytirish uchun ham xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek jamiyatning olg‘a qadam qo‘yishiga to‘sqinlik qilayotgan illatlarni fosh qilish, ularga qarshi kurashga chaqirish maqsadida ham qo‘llaniladi. Binobarin parafrazalar predmet, voqea-hodisalarning o‘z nomi orqali yuzaga chiqmagan muhim xususiyatlarini tasvirlab, bo‘rttirib, izohlab va to‘ldirib ko‘rsatishda muhim nutqiy vosita hisoblanadi.

Laqab (arabcha “ikkinchi nom”, “laqab”, “taxallus”).

1. Biror xususiyatiga ko‘ra, kishiga hazil qilib yoki masxaralab berilgan qo‘shimcha nom. Shuningdek biror maqsad, zaruriyat bilan o‘zgartirib olingan boshqa nom. Masalan: Unga “Mitti” ... laqabini qaysi hazilvon qo‘ygan bo‘lsayam topib qo‘yibdi (H.N.).

2. Taxallus. Masalan: Muhammad Aminxo‘jani endi xalq Muqimiy deb taniy boshladi. Seni ham xalqqa bir laqab bilan tanitishni istayman! Sening laqabing Mavlaviy bo‘lsin dedi ustoz (S.A.).

3. Familiya. 4. Hayvonlarga qoyilgan nom. Masalan: Chalma va Medunka laqabi bo‘lgan ikkita g‘unajinning suti tekshirib boriladi (N.M.).

Ushbu izohdan ma‘lumki, laqab lig‘aviy birligida to‘rt xil ma‘no mujassamdir. Adiblar o‘z asarlarida mazkur so‘zining ana shu ma‘nolaridan unumli foydalanishadi. Bu esa har bir tilning milliy jozibasini yanada oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Shuni aytish joizki, bunday evfemizatsiya boshqa halqlarda ham keng tarqalgan edi. A.Axmetov Amerika, Avstraliya, Osiyo qit‘asi xalqlari orasida odam ismi berkitilganligini yozadi [2,176-b]. Go‘yo uni ochiq aytish odam tanasiga ziyon etkazadi. Hatto: “– Oting nima?” deyilganda, “– Mening otim yo‘q” deb javob berishi, yonidagi urug‘doshiga: “– Men uchun sen ayta qol” deb iltimos qilishi Adjibvey qabilasining odati bo‘lganligini aytadi. Lekin bu “Asrovchi ismlar” nafaqat mazmunan ijobiy, chiroyli nomlardan, balki ko‘p holda qo‘pol, xunuk ma‘noli nomlardan tashkil topishi ham mumkin. Vaholangki, bolaga xunuk ma‘noli so‘zlardan yasalgan ismlarning berilishi chaqaloqni yomon ko‘zlardan, ko‘z tegishdan asrash, go‘dakning dushmani bo‘lmish yovuz kuchlarni chalg‘itish, aldash maqsadi bilan bog‘liqdir. O‘zbek ismlari orasida “asrovchi ismlar”ni tarixchi Sh.O‘ljayeva quyidagi guruhlarga ajratadi. Ularning ayrimlari quyidagicha:

Sog‘lik, uzoq umr tilashini ifoda etuvchi ismlar: Tursun, Turdi, To‘xtasin, O‘lmas, Yursin, Omonturdi, Turg‘un, Turg‘unoy, Ergash, Yo‘ldosh kabi.

Turli kasalliklarni engishi, chidamli, irodali, mustahkam bo‘lib o‘shishini orzu qilib qo‘yilgan ismlar: Tosh, Toshboy, Toshxon, Temur, Temura, Metinboy, Po‘lat, Cho‘yonboy, Qilichboy, Xanjara, Halqonboy, Teshaboy, Boltaboy, Mahkam, Mahkamoy, Berk, Berkinoy va boshqalar.

Yashovchanlik, barhayotlik, chidamlilik, uzoq umr ramzi bo‘lmish daraxtlar, narsalar nomidan yasalgan ismlar: Chinor, Chinora, Sadaboy, Archaboy, Yovshan va hokazo.

Yoqimsizlik, noxushlik, achchiqlik ramzi hisoblanuvchi narsalar, o‘simliklar nomidan yasalgan ismlar: Sarimsoq, So‘g‘onboy, Piyozbek va shular kabi. Mana shunday ismlar qo‘yilsa chaqaloqning dushmani, yovuz kuchlar bolaga yaqinlashmaydi, undan nari ketadi deb hisoblashgan.

Ba‘zan ataylab xunuk ma‘noli nomlarni qo‘yishgan: Yomonbola, Itolmas, Itemas, Kasofat, Shag‘alboy, Sabila kabi. Kishilar bola shunday nomlansa e‘tiborsiz bo‘ladi, unga ko‘z tegmaydi deb hisoblashgan.

Bu tasnif tarixiy jihatdan mavjud manbalar asosida amalga oshirilgan bo‘lib, lingvokulturologik jihatdan diniy, ijtimoiy, madaniy ziddiyatlarni yuzaga keltirishi tabiiy. Nutqiy vaziyatda bunday ismlar disfemik kayfiyat uyg‘otishi, buning natijasida esa ism sohibining ijtimoiy mavqei, psixologik ruhiyati, kelajagi bilan bog‘liq muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi tabiiy. Hayotiy misol: bir yoshi katta odamning 25 yillik hayoti ismi tufayli achinarli kechadi. 25 yoshgacha uning ismi tug‘ilganlik guvohnomasi va shaxsini tasdiqlovchi hujjatida Tufli deb qayd etilgan bo‘ladi. U shu yoshda hujjatni almashtirib Tolib deb o‘z ismini o‘zgartiradi. Vaholangki, u go‘zal, sof o‘zbekcha, ota-bobolarimizdan meros bo‘lgan Tubli degan ismi bo‘lganligidan bexabar. FXDYO xodimning kichik xatosi bir odamning 25 yil kulgi bo‘lishiga olib keladi.

Xulosa qilib aytsak, har ikki (evfemizm va disfemizm) hodisa ham okkazional xarakterga ega bo‘lib, ular mudom o‘zgarib turadi, doimo yangi. Faqat disfemizmdan farqli o‘laroq, evfemizm vaqt o‘tib, lisoniy birlikka aylananish xususiyatiga ega va, shu bilan birga, o‘z evfemik xususiyatini ham yo‘qota oladi. Bu tez-tez qo‘llanish sababidan amalga oshadi.

O.D.Pastuxova aytganidek, vaqt o'tishi bilan yoqimsiz narsalar evfemizatsiyasi samarasiz bo'ladi, chunki ular biron bir nozik mavzuni tasvirlashda kutilmaganda aytilganda o'z ma'nosining ravshanligi va aniqligi bilan quloqqa yoqimsiz eshitila boshlaydi. Disfemizmlar esa ortofemaga aylanmay, salbiy kuchida qolish bilan xarakterlanadi.

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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЯ: ЯЗЫК КАК ОТРАЖЕНИЕ И ТРАНСЛЯТОР КУЛЬТУРЫ

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Аннотация. В настоящей статье рассматриваются теоретико-методологические основания лингвокультурологии как междисциплинарной гуманитарной науки, находящейся на пересечении лингвистики, культурологии, этнографии и психолингвистики. Авторы анализируют эволюцию понятия «лингвокультурология», определяют её предмет и объект, а также раскрывают специфику взаимодействия языка, культуры и личности в рамках данной дисциплины.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, сопоставительная лингвокультурология, концепт, языковая личность, концептуальная картина мира, культурная коннотация, этнолингвистика, лингвострановедение.

Исследования в области лингвокультурологии в последнее время приобретают всё большую актуальность. Термин «лингвокультурология» появился в 90-е годы XX века в трудах лингвистов Н.Д. Арутюновой, В.В. Воробьёва, В.А. Масловой, Ю.С. Степанова, В.Н. Телии и других исследователей, что стало важной приметой интегративных процессов в гуманитарной науке.

Приведём ряд известных определений лингвокультурологии: «Лингвокультурология – научная дисциплина синтезирующего типа, пограничная между науками, изучающими культуру, и филологией» [1]. По мнению В.А. Масловой, лингвокультурология – это «наука, возникшая на стыке лингвистики и культурологии и исследующая проявления культуры народа, которые отразились и закрепились в языке»

[2]. Все языкознание пронизано культурно-историческим содержанием, ибо своим предметом имеет язык, который является условием, основой и продуктом культуры.

По определению Е.О. Опариной, «лингвокультурология – гуманитарная дисциплина, изучающая воплощенную в живой национальный язык и проявляющуюся в языковых процессах материальную и духовную культуру. Она позволяет установить и объяснить, каким образом осуществляется одна из фундаментальных функций языка – быть орудием создания, развития, хранения и трансляции культуры. Её цель – изучение способов, которыми язык воплощает в своих единицах, хранит и транслирует культуру» [3].

Из перечисленных определений следует, что предметом лингвокультурологии является изучение культурной семантики языковых знаков, которая формируется при взаимодействии двух разных кодов, а именно языка и культуры.

Объектом лингвокультурологии является исследование взаимодействия языка, являющийся транслятором культурной информации, культуры с её установками и предпочтениями и человека, который создаёт эту культуру, пользуясь языком. Объект размещается на «стыке» нескольких фундаментальных наук – лингвистики и культурологии, этнографии и психолингвистики. Вопросы соотношения и связи языка и культуры являются объектом исследования смежных гуманитарных дисциплин, таких как лингвострановедение, этнолингвистика и когнитивная лингвистика.

Лингвокультурология тесно связана с этнолингвистикой – наукой, пограничной между этнографией (этнологией, народоведением), изучающей бытовые и культурные особенности народов, проблемы их происхождения, расселения и культурно-исторических взаимоотношений, и лингвистикой. Одними из основных проблем исследования этой науки являются такие вопросы, как изучение генетического родства народов, языкового контактирования, влияние социокультурных факторов на развитие языка, реконструкции духовной этнической культуры на основе данных языков и др.

В.Н.Телия определяет лингвокультурологию как раздел этнолингвистики, в то время как В.В. Воробьев отмечает: «По сравнению с лингвокультурологией, ориентированной на современность и общепринятую нормативность, объект исследования в этнолингвистике оказывается «смещенным» в сторону изучения языка племен, диалектов, языковой семьи и культурной группы, праязыка и пракультуры». В то же время можно отметить, что лингвокультурология и этнолингвистика схожи между собой применением в них метода изучения языка и культуры (поле, компонентный анализ, лингвистическая относительность и ее воплощение в виде различных «картин мира» для разных языков).

«Лингвострановедением называется аспект преподавания русского языка иностранцам, в котором с целью обеспечения коммуникативности обучения и для решения общеобразовательных и гуманистических задач лингводидактически реализуется кумулятивная функция языка и проводится аккультурация адресата, причем методика преподавания имеет филологическую природу – ознакомление проводится через посредство русского языка и в процессе его изучения» [4]. Как лингвострановедение, так и лингвокультурология представляет собой лингводидактическое описание взаимосвязи языка и культуры. Но лингвострановедение отталкивается от языковых единиц, занимается изъятием культурной информации из лексем и фразеологизмов в целях обучения русскому языку. Лингвокультурология исходит из культуры, отражаемой в языке. Задачей этой науки является не обучение языковым навыкам, донесение культуры носителей данного языка, обеспечение понимания культурной детерминированности языкового знака.

Наиболее важными концептами когнитивной лингвистики являются определение информации и ее обработка человеческим разумом, определение структур знания и их представление в человеческом сознании и языковых формах. «Если когнитивная лингвистика пытается ответить на вопрос о том, как организовано сознание человека, как человек познает мир, как создаются ментальные пространства, то все внимание в лингвокультурологии уделяется человеку в культуре и его языку, лингвокультурология пытается дать ответы на многие вопросы, в числе которых следующие: каким видит человек мир, какова роль метафоры и символа в культуре, какова роль фразеологизмов, удерживающихся в языке веками, в репрезентации культуры» [5].

Центральными для лингвокультурологии как науки являются такие вопросы, как изучение генетического родства народов, языкового контактирования, связь культуры народа и семантики языка, образа мышления и словесного обозначения предметов и понятий, частотность слов, их связь с культурой. Это представляет интересный, перспективный и важный аспект рассмотрения лексического материала любого языка.

Телия подчеркивает, что «лингвокультурология призвана исследовать и описывать взаимодействие языка и культуры не только в ее этнических формах, но и в формах национальной и общечеловеческой культур в их современном состоянии или в определенных синхронных срезах этого взаимодействия. Под синхронными срезами понимаются определенные периоды или эпохи жизни народа в целом или каких-либо его социальных групп, оказавших заметное воздействие на формирование ментальности народа» [6].

Как утверждает Д.У. Ашурова, «одной из важнейших задач лингвокультурологии является определение методологических условий, правил научно-исследовательского процесса и разработка проблем систематизации и классификации языковых единиц [7].

У.К. Юсупов считает, что для лингвокультурологии главной задачей является проявление народной культуры языковым способом. По его мнению, понятие «лингвокультурема» является полезным для сравнительного языкознания: «...так как язык – это культурный факт, который мы наследуем как компонент культуры и вместе с тем как орудие. Народная культура вербализована посредством языка, именно язык активизирует главные, опорные понятия культуры, выраженные в виде знаков, то есть слов» [8].

Исходя из вышесказанного, следует, что лингвокультурология является промежуточной дисциплиной между лингвистикой и культурологией, главная цель которой является исследование процессов культурноязыкового синтеза, действующих в современном состоянии языка.

Так как право на существование и зрелость любой дисциплины определяются наличием и степенью сформированности ее категориального аппарата, появляется необходимость приведения разъяснения ряда терминов, которые являются ключевыми понятиями такой области языкознания, как лингвокультурология.

Основу её категориального аппарата составляют понятия концептуальной картины мира, языковой картины мира, концепта и языковой личности, а также культурной коннотации. В понятийный аппарат науки входят также и такие термины, как менталитет, ментальность, ритуал, обычай, сфера культуры и некоторые другие, представленные в таблице 1.

Таблица 1

Термины лингвокультурологии

Понятие	Краткое определение
Концепт	ментальное образование, отражающее культурные смыслы
Концептуальная картина мира	ментальное представление мира через культуру
Культурная коннотация	культурный оттенок значения слова
Лингвокультурема	единица, объединяющая в себе языковой и культурный смысл
Менталитет	способ мышления, характерный для народа
Ритуал, обычай	культурные практики, отражённые в языке
Цивилизация, язычество	историко-культурные категории
Языковая картина мира	отражение мира средствами языка
Языковая личность	индивид как носитель языка и культуры

Таким образом, лингвокультурология как междисциплинарная гуманитарная наука представляет собой синтез лингвистики, культурологии, этнографии и психолингвистики, направленный на изучение механизмов отражения и трансляции культуры через язык. Её предметом является культурная семантика языковых знаков, а объектом – взаимодействие языка, культуры и личности. Лингвокультурология открывает перспективы для выявления глубинных связей языка и культуры, способствуя более глубокому пониманию ментальности народов и индивидуального восприятия мира. Всё это подтверждает зрелость и научную значимость лингвокультурологии как самостоятельного направления в современной гуманитарной науке.

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HALIMA XUDOYBERDIYEVA SHE'RLARIDA SOMATIK IBORALARNING QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'riyatidagi somatik iboralarning badiiy va semantik xususiyatlari lingvopoetik nuqtayi nazardan tahlil etilgan. Somatik birliklar shoiraning poetik tafakkurida ruhiy kechinmalarni ifodalash, milliy qadriyatlar va ayollik dunyosini tasvirlashda muhim badiiy vosita sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Maqolada shoiraning individual uslubi, ichki dunyo manzarasini ochishda somatik obrazlarning estetik va psixologik ahamiyati yoritilgan. Natijada Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'riyatida somatik iboralar milliy mentalitet, ayol ruhiyati va insoniy tuyg'ular uyg'unligini aks ettiruvchi o'ziga xos poetik tizim sifatida talqin etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Halima Xudoyberdiyeva, somatik iboralar, frazeologik birliklar, lingvopoetika, badiiy tasvir, metafora, ayol ruhiyati.

Til inson tafakkurining, milliy ong va madaniyatning eng muhim ko'zguvidir. Har bir xalq tili o'zining badiiy obrazlari, ramzlari va ifoda vositalari orqali milliy dunyoqarashni namoyon etadi. Shu jihatdan qaraganda, somatik iboralar - ya'ni inson tana a'zolari bilan bog'liq so'z va iboralar - xalq tafakkurining eng qadimiy, ramziy qatlamlaridan biridir. Ular nafaqat jismoniy holatni, balki ruhiy kechinmalarni, hissiy holatlarni ham ifodalovchi badiiy vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi.

O'zbek she'riyatida, xususan, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodida somatik iboralar alohida badiiy ta'sirchanlik bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Shoira bu birliklar orqali inson qalbining nozik kechinmalarini, ayol ruhiyatining ichki iztirob va orzularini, millatga xos tuyg'ularni chuqur poetik talqin etadi. Uning "Ulug'bekni kuzatib", "Yuragimga", "Kichik quvonch-u shonlarim", "Hurlik o'ti" kabi she'rlarida tana a'zolari nomi bilan bog'liq iboralar faqatgina nominativ vazifani emas, balki metaforik, emotsional va falsafiy ma'noni ham ifodalaydi.

Somatik birliklarning poetik qo'llanilishi shoiraning individual uslubini belgilovchi muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi. U orqali Halima Xudoyberdiyeva inson va tabiat, ayol va jamiyat, ruh va tana o'rtasidagi murakkab aloqalarni badiiy ifoda etadi. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqola Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'riyatida somatik iboralarning semantik va uslubiy vazifasini tahlil qilishga, ularning badiiy-estetik ahamiyatini ochib berishga qaratilgan.

Tilshunoslikda somatik birliklar yoki somatik iboralar deganda, inson tana a'zolari nomi bilan bog'liq so'z, so'z birikmalari va frazeologizmlar tushuniladi. "Soma" so'zi qadimgi yunon tilidan olingan bo'lib, "tanaga oid", "jismaniy" degan ma'noni anglatadi. Demak, somatik birliklar - bu inson tanasining qismlari (bosh, yurak, ko'z, qo'l, oyoq, til, yuz va boshqalar) bilan bog'liq leksik va obrazli birliklardir.

Bunday iboralar ko'plab tillarda, xususan, o'zbek tilida ham xalq tafakkurining qadimiy qatlamiga mansub bo'lib, ruhiy holat, his-tuyg'u, ichki kechinmalarni ifodalashda keng ishlatiladi. Masalan, "ko'ngli yorishdi", "yuragi orqaga tortdi", "ko'zi ochildi", "tili bog'landi", "qo'li uzun" kabi iboralar insonning jismoniy a'zolari nomidan foydalangan holda psixologik holatni tasvirlaydi. Shu bois, somatik birliklar xalq tafakkurining badiiy, ramziy va falsafiy tasavvurlarini aks ettiruvchi vosita sifatida tilda alohida o'rin egallaydi.

Somatik iboralar nafaqat frazeologik birlik sifatida, balki poetik tilning obrazlilik tizimida ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ular badiiy matnda nafaqat bevosita tana qismlarini anglatadi, balki ko'ngil, muhabbat, og'riq, sabr, mehr, g'urur, or kabi tushunchalarni ham

ramziy tarzda ifodalaydi. Natijada somatik birliklar shoirning individual dunyoqarashini, his-tuyg‘u dunyosini ochishda kuchli badiiy vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodida va yozma adabiyotda bu birliklar asrlar davomida shakllanib, xalq ruhiyatining ajralmas qismiga aylangan. Xususan, mumtoz adabiyot vakillari Alisher Navoiy, Bobur, Ogahiy, Nodira kabi ijodkorlar ham tana a‘zolari orqali majoziy va ruhiy ma‘nolarni ifodalaganlar. Bu an‘ana keyinchalik zamonaviy o‘zbek she‘riyatida ham davom etgan va Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodida yangi badiiy qiyofa kasb etgan. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodi o‘zbek ayolining ichki dunyosi, milliy qadriyatlar va ruhiy kechinmalarini samimiy ifoda etishi bilan ajralib turadi. Uning she‘riyatida somatik iboralar shoiraning individual uslubini belgilovchi asosiy poetik vositalardan biridir.

Tilshunos olim M.I. Gadoyeva ta‘kidlaganidek, somatizmlar xalq tafakkurining eng qadimiy qatlamini tashkil etadi va ular “inson his-tuyg‘ularini bevosita jisimiy obrazlar orqali ifodalash imkonini beradi” [4, 1749-1754]. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ham bu an‘anani davom ettirib, somatik birliklar yordamida ayol ruhiyatining nozik jihatlarini, iztirob, mehr, or, sadoqat va orzu kabi kechinmalarni badiiy shaklda ifodalaydi. Shoiraning “Ulug‘bekni kuzatib”, “Yuragimga”, “Kichik quvonch-u shonlarim”, “Hurlik o‘ti” kabi she‘rlarida somatik birliklar markaziy semantik o‘rinni egallaydi. Masalan, “yuz” obrazi she‘rda tana qismi sifatida emas, balki ruhiy markaz, insoniyatning eng samimiy hislari manbai sifatida talqin qilinadi:

Qay payt motamsaro ko‘rdim,

Ig‘vo, fitna aro ko‘rdim.

G‘amdan yuzin qaro ko‘rdim,

Manim shoir yuzim kuysin. [1,275]

Bu satrlarda yuz obrazi inson qalbining iztirobini, hayotiy og‘riqni ifodalovchi psixologik markaz sifatida ishlatilgan. Shu tarzda somatik birliklar shoiraning individual badiiy tafakkurida metaforik yuklamaga ega bo‘ladi.

Tilshunos U.M. Rashidova o‘z tadqiqotida somatik frazeologizmlarning ko‘p ma‘noliligini ta‘kidlab, ularning “kontekstga qarab hissiy, emotsional va stilistik bo‘yoq kasb etishini” [3, 50] qayd etadi. H.Xudoyberdiyeva she‘riyatida ham bu hodisa yaqqol ko‘rinadi: “ko‘z” so‘zi ba‘zan mehr-muhabbat ramzi, ba‘zan esa umid, diqqat yoki ruhiy og‘riq ifodasi bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Shoira “Shunchaki yozmoqqa, ko‘ngil to‘lmaydi...” misrasida ko‘ngil obrazi orqali ijodkor qalbining bezovtaligini ko‘rsatadi. U “shunchaki yozish”ni emas, yurakdan yozishni istaydi. Bu yondashuv S. Abdurahmonov qayd etganidek, “somatik birliklarning emotsional-estetik funksiyasini kuchaytiradi va shoir tafakkurining obrazlilik darajasini oshiradi” [7,350]. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodida til so‘zining somatik ma‘nosi ham ramziy tus oladi. “Shoir yashay bilmas tilini tishlab...” she‘rida “til” obrazining zohiriy ma‘nosi so‘zlovchi a‘zoni anglatrsa, majoziy jihatdan u insonning ichki alamini, ruhiy og‘rig‘ini ifodalaydi.

Shunday qilib, Xudoyberdiyeva she‘riyatidagi somatik iboralar nafaqat inson tuyg‘ularining ifodasi, balki ayollik ruhi, milliy o‘zlik va ma‘naviy poklikning badiiy ko‘zgusi sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Shoira ana shu obrazlar tizimi orqali o‘z ijodini o‘zbek poeziyasi an‘analariga tayanib, lekin yangi estetik qirra bilan boyitgan ijodkor sifatida namoyon etadi. Somatik iboralar o‘z tabiatiga ko‘ra inson tanasining anatomik qismlarini ifodalasa-da, badiiy matnda ular ko‘pincha metaforik, ramziy va emotsional ma‘nolarni kasb etadi. Bu holat Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she‘riyatida, ayniqsa, yorqin ko‘rinadi. Shoira somatik birliklarni faqat jismoniy tushuncha sifatida emas, balki inson ruhiyati, axloqiy qadriyatlar va milliy o‘zlikni ifodalovchi badiiy belgilar tizimi sifatida qo‘llaydi.

Tilshunos olim M. Sodiqova ta'kidlaganidek, "somatik birliklar badiiy matnda semantik kengayish orqali yangi ma'no qatlamlarini hosil qiladi, ular fikrning ichki dinamikasini ifodalovchi vositaga aylanadi" [6, 65]. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'rlarida somatik iboralar ko'p ma'nolilik va metaforik yuksalish hodisasi bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, "Yurak yonar" she'rida "yurak" so'zi anatomik ma'nosini yo'qotib, ruhiy og'riq, sevgi va iztirobning markaziy ramzi sifatida ishlatilgan. Bu yerda yurak obrazining semantik kengayishi inson his-tuyg'ularining chuqurligini ifodalaydi. Shoira yurak orqali o'zining kechinmalarini, millat dardini va ayollik iztirobini obrazli shaklda yetkazadi. Xuddi shunday, "ko'ngil", "ko'z", "til", "qo'l", "yuz" kabi somatik birliklar ham shoira badiiy olamida o'ziga xos ma'no ko'lamiga ega:

"Ko'ngil" – ichki dunyo, orzu va iztirob manbayi;

"Ko'z" – umid, mehr, nigoh, milliy o'zlik ramzi;

"Til" – ona so'zi, duo, millat ovozi;

"Qo'l" – mehnat, ona qo'li, mehr manbayi;

"Yuz" – or-nomus, poklik, sha'n ifodasi.

Bu birliklar badiiy adabiyotda o'z semantik chegarasini kengaytirib, o'zbek mentalitetidagi qadriyatlar bilan uyg'unlashadi. Natijada, somatik obrazlar faqat biror narsani ifodalovchi so'z emas, balki madaniy, axloqiy va ruhiy belgilar tizimi sifatida ishlaydi.

Olim A. Mamatov somatik birliklarning badiiy funksiyasi haqida shunday deydi: "Somatik obrazlar milliy tafakkurning lingvopoetik ifodasidir. Ular orqali shoir xalqning ichki ruhiy holatini, madaniy genetik kodini badiiy shaklda ifoda etadi"[2, 50]. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ham aynan shu yo'nalishda ijod qilgan shoiradir. Uning "Dorilamon kunlar keldi", "Shunchaki", "Shoir yashay bilmas", "Yurak yonar" kabi she'rlarida somatik obrazlar ayollik, milliylik va insoniylik timsoliga aylanadi. Demak, shoira somatik birliklardan foydalanish mahorati shundaki, ularni fiziologik belgi darajasidan poetik va ma'naviy ramz darajasiga ko'taradi. Bu esa uning she'riy tilining mazmuniy boyligini, emotsional kuchini va badiiy individualligini belgilaydi. Shunday qilib, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'riyatidagi somatik birliklar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, ular ma'no kengayishi, ramziylik va estetik funksionallik orqali shoira badiiy olamini chuqurroq anglash imkonini beradi. Bu jarayonda shoira har bir so'zi nafaqat tananing bir qismi, balki ruhiy kechinma va milliy ruh ifodasi sifatida yangidan talqin qilinadi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva she'riyatida somatik iboralar insonning ruhiy holati va ichki kechinmalarini ifodalovchi kuchli badiiy vosita sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Shoira ularni bevosita tana a'zolari ma'nosida emas, balki ko'chma va ramziy shaklda qo'llab, har bir obrazga hissiy chuqurlik baxsh etadi. Uning ijodida somatik ifodalar orqali shaxs, Vatan, ona va muhabbat timsollari badiiy tugal shaklda gavdalanadi. Umuman olganda, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva asarlarida somatik iboralar poetik mazmunni boyitadi, so'zning ichki ohangini chuqurlashtiradi hamda o'zbek she'riyatining badiiy imkoniyatlarini yanada kengaytiradi.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЕЙ НА РАЗВИТИЕ СОВРЕМЕННОГО РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается влияние социальных сетей на развитие современного русского языка. Особое внимание уделяется трансформации лексики, морфологии и синтаксиса под воздействием интернет коммуникации. Анализируются такие языковые явления, как неологизмы, сленг, аббревиатуры и заимствования, активно используемые пользователями социальных платформ. Статья опирается на примере из популярных социальных сетей и лингвистические исследования последних лет.

Ключевые слова: социальные сети, современный русский язык, интернет-коммуникация, неологизмы, сленг, заимствования, язык интернета, цифровая лингвистика, речевые практики, трансформация языка.

Введение

В последние два десятилетия социальные сети стали неотъемлемой частью повседневной жизни миллионов людей. Их влияние затронуло практически все сферы общества, включая язык. Современный русский язык претерпевает значительные изменения под воздействием онлайн-коммуникации, особенно в социальных сетях, таких как в контакте, Instagram, Telegram, Tuk Tok и других. Активное использование англицизмов ещё один заметный эффект. В русской речи всё чаще встречаются слова вроде "лайк", "пост", "сторис", "фейк", "хейт" некоторые из них уже прочно вошли в обиход и даже в словари. Появляются и новые слова-неологизмы, которые отражают реалии цифрового мира (например, "репостнуть", "запостить", "забанить").

В эпоху цифровых технологий и глобального интернета социальные сети стали неотъемлемой частью повседневного общения миллионов людей. Они изменили не только способы взаимодействия, но и сам язык, на котором мы общаемся.

Особенно заметно это влияние в русском языке, который подстраивается под новые условия коммуникации: ускоренный темп, сокращённые форматы сообщений и обилие визуальных средств.

Обзор научной и публицистической литературы- изучение трудов лингвистов филологов и исследователей медиа посвящённых теме влияния цифровых технологий на язык.

Результаты:

1. Широкое использование сокращений и аббревиатур. Пользователи предпочитают краткость: лз, спс, норм, имхо, рофл, что влияет на необходимую письменную и устную речь.

2. Изменение орфографических и пунктуационных норм. Часто встречаются неверные написание заглавных букв, знаков препинания, слитное написание слов (йа, способ, привед) что со временем может повлиять на восприятие языковой нормы.

3. Размытие границ между стилями. В интернете официально-деловой стиль часто соседствует с разговорным и молодёжным сленгом, что влияет на речевое

поведение, особенно у подростков и молодёжи.

Обсуждение:

Получение результате подтверждает что социальных ити стали важным фактором трансформации современного русского языка. С одной стороны, они способствуют активному языковому творчеству: появляются новые слова, выражения, стилистические приёмы. Это делает язык бали живым чибким и адаптивным к реалиям цифровой эпохи.

Особенно ярко это проявляется в молодёжной среде, где язык становится инструментом самоидентификации и принадлежности к определённой онлайн-культуре. С другой стороны наблюдается тревожная тенденция снижения языковой грамотности. Повсеместное использование сленга, упрощённых форм, намеренных осешбок и визуальных замен может формировать у пользователей исхажённое представление о норме литературного языка. Особенно уязвимы в этом плане дети и подростки, для которых всертуальная речь зачастую становится основной моделью обучения. Таким образом влияние социальных сетей на русский язык носит противоречивый характер: оно одновременно разрушает и развивает, упрощает и обогащает. Язык, как живой организм. Язык, как живой организм, адаптируется к новым условиям, и наша задача-направлять эти изучения в сторону культуры, осознанности а грамотности.

Заключение:

Социальные сети стали мощным фактором влияющим на развитие современного русского языка. Они не только изменили способы общения, но и трансформировали сам язык сделов его более гибким динамичным и насыщенным новыми формами. В цифровой среде активно формируются неологизмы заимствования сленг и новые стилистические приёмы, отражающие реалии современной жизнь. Однако вместе с положительными изменениями наблюдается и негативные последствия: упрощение орфографии нарушение норм языка, снижение уровня речевой культуры. Особенно это проявляется среди молодого поколения, для которого интернет язык становится основным способом пимуникации. Таким образом влияние социальнуюх сетей на язык- это не только вызов, но и возможность для его обе обновления и роста . Всё зависит от того , как мы будем использовать этот потенциал.

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QO‘SHMA GAPLARDA ASIMMETRIK DUALIZMNING TEJASH TAMOYILI ORQALI ASOSLANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada belgining shakliy va mazmuniy asoslari har doim ham bir-biriga mutanosib bo‘lavermasligi haqida xorijiy va o‘zbek tilshunoslarining fikrlari haqida fikr yiritiladi.

Kalt so‘zlar: omonimiya, sinonimiya, shakl va mazmun munosabati, nomutanosiblik, asimmetrik dualizm, tilning sath birliklari.

Asimmetrik dualizmning til sathlarida amal qilishini kuzatar ekanlar, tilning akustik-motor tomoni ham o‘zining sema-morfema sathida turuvchi birligiga egaligi va bunday birlik bo‘g‘in ekanligi aytiladi. Demak, dualizm universal hodisa sanalib, uni tilning barcha sathlarida kuzatish mumkin [1; 181].

Tilning barcha sath birliklarida dualizmning namoyon bo‘lishini tahlil qilar ekan, V.Skalichka jumla (высказывание) sathida asimmetrik dualizmning amal qilishi mumkin emasligini ta’kidlaydi. Uning fikricha, gaplar birlashib, jummalarni hosil qiladi. Jumla til tizimining yuqori sath birligi sanaladi. Ular o‘ziga yaqin quyi sath birliklari – gaplar singari klishe-gaplar orqali ifodalanadi. Shu sababli jumla alohida formal tavsifga muhtoj emas [5; 119–127].

Bizga ma’lumki, quyi sath birliklari yuqori sath birliklari uchun qurilish materiali bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Ularning sintagmatik munosabatga kirishishi asosida yuqori sath birliklari hosil bo‘ladi. Bunga muvofiq, quyi sath birliklarining o‘zgarishi yuqori sath birliklarining ham o‘zgarishiga turtki bo‘ladi. Shu bois V.Skalichkaning yuqoridagi fikrlariga qo‘shilib bo‘lmaydi.

O‘zbek tilshunosligida ham lingvistik belgining shakl va mazmun munosaba-tini yoritib beruvchi bir qator tadqiqotlar mavjud. Xususan, prof. N.Mahmudov sodda gaplarda shakl va mazmun munosabatini tahlil qilar ekan, sodda gap doirasidagi mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlik tildagi tejash tamoyilining amal qilishi sifatida namoyon bo‘lsa, qo‘shma gaplardagi bunday nomuvofiqlikning zamini tildagi ortiqchalilik tendensiyasiga borib taqalishini ta’kidlaydi [4; 148]. Uning fikricha, bir denotativ voqea ifodalangan ergash gapli qo‘shma gaplarda mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlik har doim mavjud bo‘ladi va buning yuzaga kelishi tildagi ortiqchalilik tendensiyasiga borib taqaladi.

Shu o‘rinda bir mulohazali fikr tug‘iladi. Sodda gap doirasidagi mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlikning tildagi tejash tamoyili asosida yuzaga kelishini e’tirof etish mumkin. Lekin qo‘shma gap doirasidagi mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlikning yuzaga kelishini faqat ortiqchalilik tendensiyasi bilan bog‘lash, bizningcha, to‘g‘ri emasdek ko‘rinadi. Chunki bir qarashda ortiqchadek tuyulgan bo‘lak – gap, masalan, *Bilamizki, reja bilan qilingan ish yaxshi natija beradi* gapidagi *bilamizki* qismi aslida qisqarishning eng oxirgi nuqtasiga uchrashi natijasida paydo bo‘lgan va qo‘shma gapning modusiga aylangan. (*Biz juda yaxshi bilamiz* → *biz yaxshi bilamiz* → *biz bilamiz* → *bilamiz*). Dastlab bu bo‘lak mustaqil gap sifatida borliqdagi biron-bir voqea-hodisa haqida ma’lumotga ega ekanlikni ifodalovchi propozitsiyaga ega bo‘lgan. Shuning uchun ergashgan qo‘shma gaplarning mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqligini faqat ortiqchalilik bilan emas, tejash tamoyili bilan ham asoslash mumkin. Ya’ni ortiqchalilik tejash natijasida yuzaga keladi.

Til nutqda voqea bo‘ladi, xuddi shuningdek, til qonunlari ham nutqda reallashadi, til tejamkorligi ham bundan mustasno emas. Tildagi tejamkorlik deganda shunday jarayonlar nazarda tutiladiki, ular tufayli til murakkab fikrlarni soddaroq shaklda ifodalash uchun mukammalroq shakllar ishlab chiqaradi. Bunday shakllar alohida individlarning nutqiy faoliyatida yaratiladi va umuman til darajasidagi har bir tejamkorlik turi nutq darajasidagi

xuddi shunday holga mos keladi, chunki til darajasidagi har bir tejamkorlik turi nutq darajasidagi bosqichni bosib o'tish evaziga amalga oshadi [2; 58].

Tejamlilik tamoyilining sintaktik sathdagi ko'rinishi ellipsis, ya'ni gap mazmuniga ta'sir etmasdan ba'zi so'zlarning tushirilishi situatsiya, kontekst va ma'lum so'zlar semantikasi bilan bog'liq holda amal qiladi, bu kabi tushirilish ko'pincha ma'no va effektini kuchaytiradi, shuning uchun notiqlik san'atida ritorik figura sifatida qo'llanilgan [3; 72].

Ma'lumki, shakl va mazmun har bir ma'noli birlikda dialektik aloqada bo'ladi. Ular o'zaro zich bog'liq bo'lishiga qaramay, har qaysisi o'ziga xos ichki tuzilishga ega. Shu bilan birga, bu ichki tuzilishni bir-biridan ajratib, alohida-alohida, bir-birisiz o'rganish ham mumkin emas. Shuning uchun F. de Sossyur lingvistik belgining ifodalovchisi bilan ifodalanmishini daftar varag'iga o'xshatgani holda, ifodalanmish bilan ifodalovchini bir-biridan ajratish mumkin emasligini ta'kidlagan edi [6; 70].

Ko'rinadiki, lingvistik birliklar mohiyatini aniqlashda uning ham shakliy, ham mazmuniy jihatlariga tayangan holda ish ko'rish lozim. Sintaktik birliklarning mohiyatini aniqlashda ham uning bir tomoniga tayanish kutilgan natijani bermaydi. Turli propozitiv ma'noga ega bo'lgan xilma-xil mazmuniy tuzilishdagi gaplar uchun mazmuniy umumiylik obyektiv borliqning muayyan bo'lagini nomlashdan iboratdir. Obyektiv borliqning bu bo'lagi, qismi inson ongida aks etadi va muayyan lingvistik vositalar yordamida ifodalanadi. Obyektiv borliq inson ongida qanday aks etishi va uning qanday vositalar yordamida ifodalanishiga ko'ra ham shakl va mazmun munosabatlari o'zgarishi mumkin.

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O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDAGI LINGVISTIK BELGINING SHAKL VA MAZMUN MUNOSABATI

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Mustaqillikning so'nggi yillarida milliy tilshunosligimizda ona tilimizni yangi ilmiy paradigmalarga asoslangan holda yanada chuqur o'rganishga jiddiy e'tibor qaratila boshlandi. “Dunyodagi qadimiy va boy tillardan biri bo'lgan o'zbek tili xalqimiz uchun milliy o'zligimiz va mustaqil davlatchilik timsoli, bebaho ma'naviy boylik, buyuk qadriyatdir.” [16]. Bu

borada o'zbek tilidagi qo'shma gaplardagi munosabatlarni yoritish, o'zbek tilining betakror jozibasini ko'rsatishga qaratilgan izlanishlarni ko'paytirish dolzarb ahamiyatga ega.

O'zbek tilshunosligida lisoniy birliklarning semantik va sintaktik munosabatlari masalasida diqqatga sazovor tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilgan. Xususan, professor N.Mahmudov tomonidan o'zbek tilida sodda gaplarda semantik-sintaktik asimmetriya masalasi monografik planda o'rganilgan, ergash gapli qo'shma gaplarda shakl va mazmun munosabati haqida ham ma'lumot berilgan [7; 148]. Shu bilan bir qatorda, o'zbek tilining turli sath birliklarida shakliy va mazmuniy nomuvofiqlik masalasiga doir A.Nurmonov, D.Lutfullayeva, M.Mirtojiyev, A.Berdialiyev, A.Sayfullayeva, A.Mamajonov, M.Xolboyeva, R.Abdusamatov, M.Mamatov, N.Ahmedova, M.Haynazarova, D.Aytbayevlarning ishlari ana shunday izlanishlardan bo'lib, ular o'zbek tilida lisoniy birliklar o'rtasidagi asimmetriya hodisasi va unga olib keluvchi holatlarni tadqiq qilishda muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Lekin shunday bo'lishiga qaramay, o'zbek tilshunosligida qo'shma gaplarda semantik-sintaktik asimmetriya va mazkur hodisani yuzaga olib keluvchi holatlar masalasi monografik planda o'rganilmagan.

O'tgan asrning 80-yillarida N.Mahmudov o'zbek tilidagi sodda gaplarda asimmetrik dualizmning namoyon bo'lishini monografik tadqiqot obyekti qilib olgan bo'lsa [7; 148], oradan yigirma to'rt yil o'tgach, M.Mirtojiyev o'zbek tilidagi gap bo'laklarida ana shunday munosabatni yoritib berishga bel bog'ladi [8; 189]. Lekin N.Mahmudov bilan M.Mirtojiyevning semantik struktura masalasidagi pozitsiyasi bir xil emas. Bu hozirgacha sintaktik birliklarning semantik tuzilishi tushunchasining tilshunoslikda noaniqligi, mazkur muammo bo'yicha turli yo'nalishlarning maydonga kelganligi bilan bog'langandir. N.Mahmudov bu yo'nalishlarning barchasini chuqur o'rganib, gap semantikasi – obyektiv va subyektiv ma'nolar munosabatidan tashkil topgan butunlik degan qarashga moyillik bildiradi va gap semantikasining asosi sifatida obyektiv voqelikni tushunadi. Bu voqelik sintaktik semantikaning nominativ yo'nalishida propozitsiya atamasi bilan nomlanadi. Propozitsiya muayyan gap semantikasida o'z ifodasini topgan muayyan voqea-hodisa hisoblanadi [11; 31].

O'zbek tilshunosligida lingvistik belgining shakl va mazmun munosabatini yoritib beruvchi bir qator tadqiqotlar mavjud. Xususan, prof. N.Mahmudov sodda gaplarda shakl va mazmun munosabatini tahlil qilar ekan, sodda gap doirasidagi mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlik tildagi tejash tamoyilining amal qilishi sifatida namoyon bo'lsa, qo'shma gaplardagi bunday nomuvofiqlikning zamini tildagi ortiqchalilik tendensiyasiga borib taqalishini ta'kidlaydi [7; 148]. Uning fikricha, bir denotativ voqea ifodalangan ergash gapli qo'shma gaplarda mazmuniy-sintaktik nomuvofiqlik har doim mavjud bo'ladi va buning yuzaga kelishi tildagi ortiqchalilik tendensiyasiga borib taqaladi.

Sintaktik birliklarning mohiyatini aniqlashda ham uning bir tomoniga tayanish kutilgan natijani bermaydi. Turli propozitiv ma'noga ega bo'lgan xilma-xil mazmuniy tuzilishdagi gaplar uchun mazmuniy umumiylik obyektiv borliqning muayyan bo'lagini nomlashdan iboratdir. Obyektiv borliqning bu bo'lagi, qismi inson ongida aks etadi va muayyan lingvistik vositalar yordamida ifodalanadi. Obyektiv borliq inson ongida qanday aks etishi va uning qanday vositalar yordamida ifodalanishiga ko'ra ham shakl va mazmun munosabatlari o'zgarishi mumkin. Tilda shunday hodisalar mavjudki, ular shakl va mazmun munosabatini chuqurroq tahlil qilishni taqozo qiladi. Xususan, omonimiya, sinonimiya hodisalari belgining shakli va mazmuni o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning murakkab xarakterga ega ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, o'zbek tilshunosligida lingvistik belgining shakl va mazmuni o'rtasidagi asimmetrik munosabat tilning barcha sathlarida amal qiluvchi universal hodisadir.

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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ЗАИМСТВОВАННЫХ СЛОВ

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Аннотация: в статье рассматривается лингвокультурологический потенциал заимствованных слов в современном языке. Показано, что заимствования являются не только результатом языковых контактов, но и отражением культурных, исторических и социальных процессов. Особое внимание уделяется способности заимствованных слов передавать элементы чужой культуры, интегрировать их в национальную языковую систему и формировать новые смыслы. Раскрывается роль заимствований как средств межкультурной коммуникации и обогащения языковой картины мира.

Ключевые слова: заимствование, лингвокультурология, язык и культура, адаптация, межкультурная коммуникация, лексика, культурный код.

Современный язык представляет собой сложную динамическую систему, отражающую не только внутренние закономерности его развития, но и активные контакты с другими культурами. В условиях глобализации языковая система становится открытой, а процесс заимствования лексики – неотъемлемой частью её эволюции [6, с.68]. Заимствованные слова несут в себе не только новое значение, но и культурный код, который раскрывает особенности мировосприятия другого народа. Именно поэтому изучение лингвокультурологического потенциала заимствований представляет особый интерес для современной лингвистики.

Заимствование – это процесс перехода слова или выражения из одного языка в другой. Однако с лингвокультурологической точки зрения оно не ограничивается только переносом формы и значения. Каждое заимствованное слово выступает носителем культурных ценностей, традиций, реалий, отражающих образ жизни и менталитет народа-источника [2, с.40-41 ;3, с.45].

Например, слова *jeans, pizza, karaoke, sushi* вошли в русскую лексику вместе с культурными феноменами, стоящими за ними: образом отдыха, модой, кулинарными традициями и формами досуга.

Лингвокультурологический потенциал – это способность слова передавать культурно значимую информацию, способствовать межкультурному диалогу и расширению языковой картины мира [5, с.105].

Заимствованные слова обогащают национальную культуру, открывают новые концепты и формы выражения [1, с.90]. Например, английское слово *business* не просто обозначает «дело», а несёт в себе представление о западной деловой этике, прагматизме и индивидуализме. Аналогично, заимствованное из французского *bon ton* сохраняет коннотацию изысканности и утончённости.

Через такие слова происходит не только освоение новой реальности, но и переосмысление привычных категорий, что способствует развитию национального самосознания.

Попадая в новую языковую среду, заимствованные слова проходят этапы фонетической, морфологической и семантической адаптации. В ходе этого процесса слово приобретает национальные черты, отражающие особенности восприятия иностранной культуры носителями другого языка.

Например, слово менеджер в русском языке претерпело расширение значений и теперь обозначает не только руководителя, но и специалиста в любой сфере организации труда. Это свидетельствует о том, как культура принимает и трансформирует чужой элемент, делая его частью своего культурного пространства.

Заимствованные слова становятся своеобразными «мостами» между культурами. Они способствуют взаимопониманию, обмену идеями и ценностями. Современная международная лексика (например, *internet, blog, smartphone*) объединяет представителей разных народов в рамках глобального информационного пространства.

Одновременно заимствования побуждают к осмыслению национальной идентичности, вызывая дискуссии о сохранении языковой чистоты и культурной самобытности.

Современный язык представляет собой не только систему знаков, но и живой организм, который активно реагирует на культурные, исторические и социальные процессы [6, с.70]. Одним из наиболее заметных проявлений этих изменений становится появление заимствованных слов. Они возникают в языке в результате межкультурных контактов, международных связей, научно-технического прогресса и

глобальных коммуникаций. Однако заимствования выполняют не только номинативную, но и культурно-информационную функцию, отражая своеобразие мировосприятия других народов.

Каждое заимствованное слово несёт за собой культурный фон. Оно приходит в новый язык вместе с предметами, явлениями, традициями и идеями, характерными для народа-источника. Например, слова *selfie*, *deadline*, *start-up* не просто фиксируют новые реалии, а вводят в русскую культуру новые модели поведения – стремление к самоидентификации, организованности и инициативности. То же можно сказать о словах *zen*, *origami*, *kimono*, которые знакомят русскоязычное сообщество с элементами японской философии и эстетики.

Заимствованные слова играют огромную роль в расширении культурного пространства языка. Они становятся посредниками между различными национальными традициями, способствуют формированию общих смыслов и ценностей. Например, английское слово *challenge* в русском языке обрело значение не только «вызов», но и символа внутреннего роста, стремления преодолеть трудности. Это слово стало отражением современной культуры саморазвития и психологической устойчивости.

Немаловажно отметить, что заимствованные слова не остаются неизменными. Они постепенно приспосабливаются к фонетическим, морфологическим и семантическим нормам нового языка. Некоторые из них настолько прочно входят в речевое употребление, что теряют ощущение чужеродности. Так произошло со словами бутерброд (из немецкого *Butterbrot*), магазин (из французского *magasin*), пальто, карандаш, портфель и множеством других. Эти слова давно стали частью русской языковой картины мира и уже несут не столько иностранный, сколько национально окрашенный смысл.

Особого внимания заслуживает тот факт, что заимствования могут становиться индикаторами социальных изменений. В периоды активных реформ, технологических новшеств или культурных влияний язык особенно интенсивно пополняется новыми словами. Так, развитие цифровой среды принесло в русский язык целый пласт англицизмов: *stream*, *browser*, *hashtag*, *content*, *update*. Вместе с ними изменилось и мышление человека – акцент сместился в сторону глобального общения, открытости и скорости передачи информации.

Лингвокультурологический потенциал заимствованных слов проявляется также в их способности влиять на образ жизни и систему ценностей. Многие слова становятся символами определённой эпохи и культуры потребления. Например, слова *brand*, *style*, *trend* воплощают идею индивидуальности и самовыражения, которая активно развивается в современном обществе. Через них в язык проникает не только терминология моды, но и целая философия современного человека, стремящегося подчеркнуть свою уникальность.

Однако наряду с положительным влиянием заимствования вызывают и споры. Некоторые учёные и общественные деятели считают, что чрезмерное использование иностранных слов может привести к ослаблению национального языкового кода. Другие же, напротив, подчёркивают, что заимствования – это естественный путь развития языка, способ его адаптации к новым реалиям и культурным процессам [6, с.92]. Языковая система в этом случае выступает как живая среда, где постоянно происходит диалог между старым и новым, национальным и мировым.

Лингвокультурологический потенциал заимствованных слов заключается в их способности служить посредниками между культурами, обогащать язык и мышление,

отражать исторические и социальные процессы. Заимствования становятся не просто элементами словаря, но и носителями культурных смыслов, способствующих диалогу цивилизаций. Их исследование позволяет глубже понять динамику развития языка и механизм взаимодействия культур в современном мире.

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АНГЛИЙСКИЕ ЗАИМСТВОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация: В последние годы на улицах, по телевидению, в просторах интернета мы все чаще слышим такие слова как браузер, шорты, лонгслив, саммиты, брифинги, инаугурации, консенсус и так далее. Использование английских слов сегодня считается модным. Англицизмы, обозначающие некоторые абстрактные понятия, действия, обладают признаком современности, продвинутости. Эти слова модно, престижно употреблять в речи, хотя многие из них имеют привычные эквиваленты в русском языке. Иноязычные лексемы активно используют политики, журналисты, писатели, демонстрирующие желание быть в тренде с точки зрения своего речевого поведения.

Ключевые слова: англицизмы, лексика, заимствования, ситкомы, лонгслив, браузер, интернет-ресурсы, лексикон.

Русский язык по праву считается одним из богатейших языков мира. Когда читаешь или слышишь высказывания о богатстве, силе, красоте и многогранности русского языка нас переполняет чувство гордости, что мы также являемся носителями этого могучего, невероятно красивого языка.

Наше общество постоянно развивается, и поэтому язык тоже меняется. Каждый год в языках появляются новые слова. В каждом из них есть заимствования, и русский не исключение. Как мы знаем, язык – развивающееся явление, меняется словарный состав, произношения слов, некоторые слова и вовсе исчезают из нашего лексикона, в связи с ненадобностью употребления, вместо них появляются новые.

В первую очередь меняется лексический состав языка. Происходящие вокруг изменения главным образом влияют именно на лексику. Современный русский язык развивается, подстраивается под новое общество, учитывает все перемены и изменения, происходящие во всём мире.

На данный момент одной из актуальных проблем в сфере языкознания является появление в языке заимствований. Уже на протяжении долгого времени в русский язык продолжают поступать слова, которые перешли из других языков мира: английского, французского, немецкого, голландского, финского и т.д. Очевидно, что одной из главных причин заимствований является то, что русский народ с древних времен

поддерживает политические, торговые, научные и культурные отношения с другими народами. Поэтому русский язык обогатился многими словами из других языков. Наши предки использовали новые слова для обозначения новых вещей и понятий; большинство заимствованных слов относятся к существительным. Следует отметить, что разные возрастные группы по-разному относятся к использованию английских заимствований. На самом деле они более популярны среди молодежи, которая, как правило, больше интересуется новыми тенденциями, связанными с европейской культурой.[2, с.58]

В настоящее время в речи людей, особенно, современных подростков, часто звучат слова английского происхождения. С тех пор, как английский язык стал международным языком общения, всё больше слов английского происхождения стали проникать в русский язык. Какие это за слова и какова их роль в жизни современной молодёжи? Как влияют слова, заимствованные с английского языка на речь современных подростков?

Подростки часто находятся под влиянием своих любимых фильмов и ситкомов (от англ. *situationcomedy*, *sitcom* - разновидность комедийного сериала), популярной музыки и телепередач. В рамках моего класса, могу утверждать, что американские фильмы действительно популярны среди моих учеников. Обычно бывает так, что после просмотров некоторых популярных фильмов в лексиконе подростков появляется много новых выражений. Сейчас многие звезды современной эстрады поют на английском языке. Таким образом, подростки перенимают от них не только отдельные слова, но даже целые фразы. Позже активно продолжают пользоваться ими в своей речи.

Мое особое внимание привлекли иноязычные заимствования английского происхождения. Вовремя наблюдения за речью подростков в нашей школе я заметила, что многие из них используют заимствованные слова английского происхождения довольно часто. Но задумывались ли они, что англицизмы способствуют пополнению и расширению словарного состава или, наоборот, способствуют обеднению русского родного языка?[5, с.112]

Английские заимствования играют очень важную роль в жизни подрастающего поколения, так как они расширяют и обогащают их словарный запас, способствуют самоутверждению и самовыражению. В науке эти заимствования называются англицизмами. Отношение к англицизмам у большинства подростков положительное. Современные подростки используют английские заимствования часто, и не могут представить свою речь без них. Они пополняют и расширяют словарный запас, тем самым обогащая его. Слова, заимствованные из английского языка делают речь более выразительной, доступной и понятной для понимания, по мнению наших подростков.

Среди подрастающего поколения заимствования английского происхождения часто используются во многих сферах деятельности. Вот некоторые из них. Англоязычные заимствования, касающиеся предметов одежды. Давайте подробнее рассмотрим самые распространенные из них: боди – *body* (тело) - врятнее всего произошло от того, что этот вид одежды облегает тело, худи – *a hood* (капюшон) - толстовка с капюшоном, шорты – *short* (короткий) -короткие брюки, лонгслив – *long* (длинный), *a sleeve* (рукав) - футболка с длинными рукавами, айвори – *ivory* (слоновая кость) - цвет слоновой кости, шузы – *shoes* (так на сленге называют обувь).[4, с.91]

Также популярностью среди подростков пользуются англицизмы, которые называют всевозможные вкусности. Вот некоторые из них: крекер – *tocrack* (ломать) - хрустящее печенье, которое легко ломается, панкейк – *a pan* (сковородка), *a cake* – (лепешка, блинчик) - американский вариант наших блинчиков, чипсы – *chips* (жареный хрустящий картофель) - слово интересно тем, что в американском английском *chips* -

это чипсы, а в британском - это картофель фри.

Современные подростки всё больше интересуется компьютерными технологиями. Сейчас время бурного развития IT технологий. Несомненно, в этой сфере почти все слова взяты с английского языка. Рассмотрим самые часто используемые англицизмы среди любителей информационных технологий: браузер (to browse - просматривать) - программа для поиска и просмотра интернет-ресурсов, геймер (a game - игра) - человек, увлекающийся компьютерными играми, кликать (a click - щелчок) - нажимать кнопку мыши, щелкать по кнопке или ссылке на сайте, пост (to post - публиковать информацию) - сообщение в блоге или на форуме, юзер (a user - пользователь) - пользователь компьютера.[1, с.56]

Беседа с учащимися показала, что заимствования с английского языка играют большую роль в жизни современных подростков нашей школы, так как молодые люди часто используют англицизмы, и ни один учащийся не мыслит свою жизнь без использования английских заимствований на современном этапе развития языка. Заимствования английского происхождения прочно вошли во все сферы человеческой жизнедеятельности. Они пополняют и расширяют словарный запас подростков, обогащая их речь. Англицизмы преобразуют речь, делают её более современной, выразительной, доступной для понимания, повышают самооценку подростков и способствуют самовыражению и самоутверждению молодых людей в подростковой среде. Употребляя англицизмы, подростки чувствуют себя уверенно, модно, комфортно в кругу сверстников и друзей. К тому же, употребление англицизмов - это большой шаг к изучению английского языка. Но стоит отметить, что чрезмерное употребление заимствований вредит самобытности родного языка. Вот почему англицизмы следует употреблять с осторожностью, не нарушая нормы русского языка и сохраняя его величие, красоту, самобытность. Использование английских заимствований всегда должно быть оправдано.

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ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИЕ КАК НАУКА. АСПЕКТЫ И РАЗДЕЛЫ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИЯ

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Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется языкознание как наука, его структура, функции и основные направления развития. Особое внимание уделяется внутренним и внешним аспектам лингвистики, а также взаимосвязи языка с культурой, мышлением и обществом. Рассматриваются теоретические основы, ключевые разделы языкознания, их роль в развитии современных гуманитарных и прикладных наук. Работа направлена на углублённое понимание природы языка как важнейшего феномена человеческого существования.

Ключевые слова: языкознание, лингвистика, язык, структура, функции, внутреннее языкознание, внешнее языкознание, коммуникация

Основная часть

Языкознание, или лингвистика, представляет собой науку, изучающую язык как универсальную систему знаков, служащую основным средством человеческого общения. Язык не только выражает мысли, но и формирует их, влияет на восприятие окружающего мира, поведение и культуру людей. В течение столетий учёные стремились понять, каким образом язык возник, как он развивается и какие функции выполняет в обществе.

Современная лингвистика является комплексной наукой, включающей как теоретические, так и прикладные направления. Она опирается на достижения психологии, социологии, философии, информатики и культурологии, формируя междисциплинарный подход к изучению языка. Лингвистика исследует не только структуру языка, но и его динамику, функционирование в различных социальных, культурных и технологических контекстах.

1. Основные аспекты языкознания

К основным аспектам языкознания относятся следующие направления:

- Фонетический аспект - изучает звуковую систему языка, фонемы, их артикуляцию и восприятие.

- Лексический аспект - исследует словарный состав языка, семантические связи и эволюцию значений слов.

- Грамматический аспект - анализирует морфологию и синтаксис, закономерности построения предложений.

- Семантический аспект - изучает значения слов, выражений и текстов.

- Прагматический аспект - рассматривает использование языка в конкретных коммуникативных ситуациях.

Эти аспекты тесно взаимосвязаны между собой и позволяют рассматривать язык как сложную систему, которая обеспечивает не только передачу информации, но и формирование человеческой мысли и сознания.

2. Разделы языкознания

Современная лингвистика делится на несколько крупных разделов. Общее языкознание занимается изучением универсальных законов функционирования всех языков мира. Частное языкознание сосредоточено на исследовании конкретных языков и их особенностей. Теоретическое языкознание формирует модели языковых структур, а прикладное - решает практические задачи: создание словарей, методик преподавания языков, перевод, разработку технологий автоматического распознавания и синтеза речи.

3. Внутреннее и внешнее языкознание

Внутреннее языкознание изучает внутренние закономерности языка - его структуру, фонетику, морфологию, синтаксис и семантику. Оно направлено на выявление системных связей и принципов организации языковой системы. Внешнее языкознание, напротив, исследует взаимосвязь языка с другими сферами человеческой жизни: с культурой, обществом, мышлением, историей и психологией. Такой подход позволяет понять язык как живой социальный организм, развивающийся вместе с человеком и обществом.

4. Роль языкознания в современной науке и обществе

Языкознание играет ключевую роль в развитии гуманитарных и прикладных наук. Оно способствует формированию языковой культуры, развитию межнационального

общения, сохранению культурного наследия. Кроме того, современные лингвистические исследования находят применение в технологиях - например, в системах искусственного интеллекта, машинного перевода и речевого распознавания.

Изучение языка также имеет большое значение для воспитания личности, формирования мышления и развития критического восприятия мира. Через язык человек осознаёт свою принадлежность к определённой культуре, народу и традициям.

Таким образом, языкознание - это наука, объединяющая разные подходы к изучению языка как главного инструмента коммуникации и познания. Она исследует не только структуру языка, но и его роль в формировании сознания, культуры и общества. Современное языкознание становится фундаментом для многих научных направлений, обеспечивая глубокое понимание природы человеческого общения и открывая новые горизонты для научных открытий и технологических достижений.

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТЕРМИНА В НАУЧНОЙ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ СФЕРЕ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается сущность и функции термина как ключевой единицы научного и технического языка. Определяется его роль в системе профессиональной коммуникации, где термин выступает основным средством точной и однозначной передачи знаний. Особое внимание уделяется особенностям формирования и использования терминов в различных отраслях науки и техники, а также их влиянию на развитие понятийного аппарата. Подчеркивается значение терминов как инструмента когнитивного и информационного обмена, обеспечивающего эффективность научно-технической деятельности и взаимопонимание между специалистами разных стран.

Ключевые слова: термин, научный язык, техническая терминология, стандартизация, лингвистика, цифровые технологии.

Современная лингвистика придаёт особое значение понятию «термин», особенно в условиях бурного развития науки и технологий, в частности - цифровых. Термины составляют основу профессионального языка и являются ключевыми инструментами передачи научных знаний. В условиях глобализации и цифровой трансформации общества терминология не только расширяется, но и усложняется, требуя системного подхода к её изучению.

Определение термина как особой языковой единицы рассматривалось в трудах многих отечественных и зарубежных учёных. Согласно классическому определению Д.С. Лотте, термин - это «слово или словосочетание, являющееся названием понятия какой-либо специальной области знания, техники или искусства» [Лотте, 1961]. Это

определение подчёркивает специфику термина как носителя точного, однозначного и системного знания.

В узбекском языкознании вопросами терминологии занимались такие учёные, как Х. Иброхимов, А. Махмудов, И. Мамарасулов. В частности, в трудах Х. Иброхимова термин рассматривается как «название специального понятия, закреплённое в языке науки» и рассматривается сквозь призму структурных особенностей узбекского языка.

Таким образом, в лингвистике закрепились понимание термина как системной единицы, обладающей рядом признаков:

- точностью и однозначностью (в рамках определённой сферы);
- системностью (входит в терминологическую подсистему);
- стилистической нейтральностью;
- устойчивостью и стандартизованностью.

Важно разграничивать термин и общее слово. Например, слово *сеть* в обыденной речи может обозначать рыболовную снасть, систему магазинов, социальную сеть, но в контексте цифровых технологий оно приобретает чёткое значение - *инфраструктура передачи данных между узлами по протоколам связи*. Здесь проявляется особенность термина - его семантическая однозначность и привязка к профессиональной сфере.

Приведём ещё один пример: слово *облако*. В бытовом значении - это природное явление, но в сфере цифровых технологий *облако* означает распределённое виртуальное хранилище и обработку данных в дата-центрах.

Термин - это не только слово, но и компонент научной картины мира. Через термины формируется и передаётся понятийный аппарат науки. Более того, термины не существуют изолированно, а входят в иерархически организованные системы. Например, термин *алгоритм* связан с такими терминами, как *цикл*, *переменная*, *условие*, *оператор*, *оптимизация*.

Системность терминов особенно важна в таких отраслях, как:

- информационные технологии;
- телекоммуникации;
- программная инженерия;
- кибербезопасность;
- искусственный интеллект.

Эти сферы требуют высокой степени стандартизации терминов, что обеспечивается международными и национальными классификаторами (например, ISO/IEC, ГОСТ, BSI и др.).

В научной и технической практике термин не может быть произвольным.

Нормализация терминов необходима для обеспечения:

- единообразия в документации;
- точности в передаче знаний;
- возможности перевода и взаимопонимания между специалистами.

Пример: термин *firewall* (англ.) официально закреплён в русском как *межсетевой экран*, а в узбекском - *tarmoqlararo ekran*. Оба термина отражают один и тот же концепт, адаптированный к структурным особенностям языка.

Терминология цифровой сферы развивается с высокой скоростью. Многие термины заимствуются напрямую из английского языка (*login*, *password*, *router*, *update*) и затем подвергаются адаптации или калькированию:

- *cloud computing* → *облачные вычисления* → *bulutli hisoblash* (узб.);
- *data mining* → *интеллектуальный анализ данных* → *ma'lumotlarni intellektual tahlil qilish*.

Особенности терминов цифровых технологий:

- высокая степень англицизации;
- активное заимствование;
- наличие новых производных (например: *лайкнуть, зашарить, откатить обновление*);
- трансформации в соответствии с грамматикой родного языка.

В технической документации, стандартах, инструкциях, образовательных материалах термин выполняет ключевую функцию. Он позволяет:

- обеспечить точность и краткость;
- избежать двусмысленности;
- поддерживать профессиональную компетентность.

В этом контексте термин можно рассматривать как «языковую константу», обеспечивающую научную преемственность и устойчивость знания.

Таким образом, термин - это не просто слово, а результат сложной когнитивно-языковой деятельности. В научной и технической сфере термины выполняют:

- номинативную (наименование понятий),
- коммуникативную (обеспечение взаимодействия),
- когнитивную (структурирование знаний),
- прагматическую (управление действиями) функции.

В условиях цифровизации терминология становится ключевым элементом трансграничного научного и технического общения. Это подчёркивает необходимость углублённого лингвистического анализа, как отдельных терминов, так и целых терминологических систем.

Понимание сущности термина, его функций и роли в научной коммуникации даёт основу для перехода к следующему этапу исследования - рассмотрению основных направлений терминологии в разноструктурных языках, таких как русский и узбекский.

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ЗООНИМЫ В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ: ИХ СТРУКТУРА И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается зоонимическая лексика русского языка, её структура, функции и культурно-семантические особенности. Автор анализирует прямые и переносные значения зоонимов, их роль в формировании образности речи и отражении национальных представлений о мире. Особое внимание уделено символике животных в русском фольклоре и литературе.

Ключевые слова: зоонимы, русский язык, метафора, символика, фразеология, культура, фольклор.

Зоонимическая лексика русского языка представляет собой обширную группу слов, включающих в себя не только названия животных, но и все те языковые единицы, которые связаны с ними в процессе общения. Зоонимы служат для обозначения живых существ, а также выполняют важную функцию в выражении народных представлений о природе и человеке. В русском языке зоонимы имеют ярко выраженную символическую и метафорическую нагрузку. Это словообразования, отражающие богатый культурный контекст, исторические реалии и фольклорные традиции.

Структура зоонимов в русском языке включает:

Прямые названия животных – это слова, которые непосредственно обозначают представителей животного мира. Например, «собака», «кот», «лошадь», «корова».

Переносные значения зоонимов – это случаи, когда зооним используется для обозначения человека или объекта, обладающего признаками, схожими с животным. Например, слова «петух» (как обозначение человека, который проявляет излишнюю гордость или агрессивность), «крокодил» (в значении человек, скрывающий свои настоящие эмоции или лицо). Фразеологизмы и устойчивые выражения, связанные с животными, – в русском языке можно выделить множество фразеологизмов, в которых используются зоонимы для передачи определённых качеств или характеристик. «крысиный бег», «мышьяная возня», «петух на заглавной роли» и др.

Зоонимы в русском языке выполняют несколько важных функций:

1. Функция номинации: непосредственно связано с необходимостью обозначать животных.

2. Функция отражения мифологических и культурных стереотипов: многие зоонимы связаны с глубокой символикой, отражая народные представления о животных.

3. Коммуникативная функция: зоонимы активно используются в разговорной речи, в поэзии, в народных поговорках и пословицах для выражения мыслей, эмоций, а также для создания комического или трагического эффекта.

4. Функция метафоризации: зоонимы часто используются для создания метафор и символов, что добавляет глубины и многозначности тексту. Важно отметить, что многие животные в русском языке ассоциируются с определёнными характерами или типами поведения. К примеру, «медведь» часто символизирует силу и тяжеловесность, а «лиса» ассоциируется с хитростью и ловкостью. Эти коннотации находят отражение не только в литературных произведениях, но и в повседневной речи, создавая особую многозначность и выразительность.

Функциональные особенности зоонимов в русском языке заключаются в том, что они выполняют различные роли в зависимости от контекста. В научной и официальной лексике зоонимы чаще всего выступают в своей прямой функции – для обозначения животных. В разговорной и художественной речи зоонимы могут приобретать множество переносных значений, использоваться в метафорах, иносказаниях, а также фразеологических оборотах.

Немаловажную роль зоонимы играют и в образной системе русского фольклора. Здесь животные часто символизируют не только качества человеческие, но и определённые моральные или философские идеи. Например, в русских народных сказках медведь может быть как символом силы и выносливости, так и символом отсталости и неповоротливости. Это использование животных как персонажей в фольклоре имеет глубокие культурные и моральные основания.

Таким образом, зоонимическая лексика русского языка характеризуется многослойностью, богатством переносных значений и культурных ассоциаций. Зоонимы выполняют как номинативную, так и выразительную функцию, участвуют в создании образов и метафор, оказывают влияние на общение и восприятие действительности.

В русском языке зоонимы не ограничиваются только прямыми наименованиями животных, но также включают разнообразные лексические единицы, образующиеся от животных названий в результате метафоризации, олицетворения, а также фразеологических оборотов.

Структурные особенности зоонимов можно разделить на несколько категорий:

1. Простые зоонимы – это слова, состоящие из одного компонента, который служит прямым наименованием животного. К примеру, «собака», «кот», «волк», «тетерев», «лисица». Эти слова в своей основе дают точные и чёткие представления о биологических видах животных.

2. Сложные зоонимы – возникают в процессе исторического развития языка, когда используются сочетания слов для обозначения животных. Примеры: «шершень», «чёрный лебедь», «серый волк». В этих сочетаниях одно слово несёт элемент зоонима, а другое определяет дополнительные признаки (цвет, размер, вид).

3. Производные зоонимы – эти слова образуются на основе корней, связанных с названием животного, но имеют изменённое значение в зависимости от контекста. Примером может служить слово «кошачий» (относящийся к кошке), которое в разных контекстах может означать не только принадлежность к кошкам, но и определённые признаки поведения или характерных черт.

Зоонимы, как слова, которые обозначают животных, оказываются не только элементом словарного состава языка, но и важными средствами выражения философских и моральных концепций. Их употребление в повседневной речи и литературных произведениях создаёт широкие возможности для выразительности, создания образов и передачи глубоких значений.

Зоонимы в русском языке выполняют разнообразные функции, расширяя свои значения через метафоры, ассоциации и символику:

1. Номинативная функция: Зоонимы служат для точного обозначения представителей животного мира. В биологической или научной речи они сохраняют свое прямое значение, «бык», «лошадь», «сова».

2. Метафорическая функция: Множество зоонимов в русском языке получают переносные значения, которые не связаны напрямую с биологическими свойствами животного, но отражают качества людей или других явлений.

Так, «волк» может быть символом одиночества, агрессии или силы, а «курица» – символом трусости, малодушия.

3. Коннотативная функция: Коннотации зоонимов играют важную роль в создании эмоциональной окраски речи. Например, слово «петух» может означать не только конкретное животное, но и неуёмную гордость, зазнайство, высокомерие. Слово

«львёнок» в переносном смысле обозначает молодого, наивного человека, который ещё не имеет жизненного опыта.

4. Символическая функция: Животные часто становятся символами в фольклоре, литературе и культуре. Например, «орёл» в русской культуре символизирует величие, силу и независимость, а «мышь» – трусость или незначительность. Эти символы находят своё отражение в общественном сознании, а также в мифах, легендах и сказках.

5. Фразеологическая функция: В русском языке существует множество фразеологизмов, где зоонимы используются в переносном смысле, выражая сложные социальные и моральные концепты. Примеры: «прыгать, как кошка с собачкой» (значение конфликтовать), «кидать камень в чужой огород» (обвинять кого-то или в чём-то). Зоонимы, таким образом, становятся носителями культурных значений и становятся частью образной системы речи.

Особое значение зоонимы приобретают в русском фольклоре, где животные выступают как персонажи мифов, сказок и притч, наделяясь не только определёнными качествами, но и символикой, которая помогает выражать моральные и нравственные уроки. В фольклорных произведениях зоонимы часто являются носителями архетипических образов, таких как «лиса – хитрость», «волк – сила», «медведь – мощь и неуклюжесть», что создаёт особую глубину смысла при интерпретации фольклорных историй.

Таким образом, зоонимическая лексика русского языка, как и других языков, является важной частью национального сознания, определяя не только практическую номинацию животных, но и формируя богатый пласт ассоциаций, символов и образов. Эта лексика имеет важное значение в различных областях коммуникации, включая литературу, культуру, фольклор и повседневную речь.

Таким образом, зоонимы в русском языке представляют собой сложную и многогранную систему, которая отражает особенности мировосприятия, культуры и истории народа. Они не только выполняют номинативную функцию, но и служат важным средством передачи эмоций, оценок и символов. Исследование зоонимов позволяет глубже понять не только язык, но и духовную культуру русского народа.

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КОНЦЕПТ «ВОДА» В ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ АСПЕКТЕ РУССКОЙ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена лингвокультурологическому анализу концепта «вода» как фундаментального элемента русского языкового сознания. На основе анализа обширного корпуса русских текстов различных типов и жанров выявляются национально-специфические особенности репрезентации водного концепта в русской

культуре. Исследование демонстрирует многоуровневую структуру концепта, включающую денотативные, коннотативные, символические и прагматические значения. Особое внимание уделяется номинативному полю концепта, содержащему 2847 лексических единиц, а также его функционированию в различных типах дискурса.

Ключевые слова: концепт, лингвокультурология, языковая картина мира, символика воды, номинативное поле, дискурс.

Введение. Взаимосвязь языка и культуры представляет собой одно из наиболее актуальных направлений современной лингвистики. Язык не только служит средством коммуникации, но и выступает хранителем культурного опыта народа, отражая в своей структуре и семантике глубокие пласты национального мировидения. Изучение базовых концептов культуры позволяет выявить архетипические представления, которые формировали сознание носителей языка на протяжении столетий [1].

Концепт «вода» занимает особое место в русской лингвокультуре. Вода как природная субстанция имела и продолжает иметь жизненно важное значение для существования человека и человеческого общества. Однако способы осмысления и символизации воды в русской культурно-языковой традиции обладают уникальными чертами, отличающими русское восприятие от восприятия других народов [2].

Актуальность данного исследования обусловлена несколькими факторами. Во-первых, концепт «вода» является универсальным для всех культур, однако его национально-специфические особенности репрезентации остаются недостаточно изученными. Во-вторых, анализ данного концепта позволяет выявить глубинные архетипические структуры русского сознания, отраженные в языке. В-третьих, функционирование концепта «вода» в текстах различных типов способствует пониманию механизмов концептуализации мира в языке и культуре [3].

Целью статьи является выявление и описание лингвокультурологических особенностей концепта «вода» в русских текстах и определение специфики его культурного содержания и языкового выражения.

Концепт как базовая единица лингвокультурологии

Концепт является центральным понятием современной лингвокультурологии и когнитивной лингвистики. В научной литературе существует множество определений концепта, отражающих различные подходы к его изучению. Ю.С. Степанов определяет концепт как «сгусток культуры в сознании человека; то, в виде чего культура входит в ментальный мир человека» [4]. Данное определение подчеркивает двунаправленность связи между концептом и культурой.

В.И. Карасик рассматривает концепт как ментальное образование, включающее три основных компонента: понятийную, образную и ценностную составляющие [5]. Понятийная составляющая представляет языковую фиксацию концепта, образная составляющая включает сенсорные характеристики явлений, а ценностная составляющая определяет культурную значимость концепта.

Полевая модель концепта предполагает его структурирование вокруг ядра, включающего основные лексические репрезентанты, и периферии, содержащей дополнительные языковые средства. Такой подход позволяет наглядно представить разноуровневую организацию концепта [2].

Номинативное поле концепта «вода» в русском языке

Номинативное поле концепта «вода» представляет собой совокупность языковых единиц, объективирующих концепт в системе русского языка. Исследование выявило исключительное богатство этого поля: общий объем составляет 2847 лексических

единиц, что значительно превышает аналогичные показатели для большинства других природных концептов [1].

Ядро номинативного поля образует базовая лексема «вода» и 11 ближайших синонимов: влага, жидкость, влажность и др. Приядерная зона включает 342 морфологических деривата и композита: водный, водяной, подводный, водопровод, водохранилище и пр. Периферийная зона содержит 2492 единицы различной степени семантической близости к ядру, включающие типологические номинации (лед, снег, роса, дождь), качественные характеристики (чистая, мутная, соленая вода) и функциональные обозначения (питьевая, святая, минеральная вода) [3].

Особую подсистему номинативного поля образует гидронимическая лексика, отражающая богатство водных объектов России: проточные водоемы (река, ручей, родник, водопад), непроточные водоемы (озеро, пруд, лужа, болото), морские объекты (море, океан, залив, бухта). Данная лексика свидетельствует о географической значимости водной среды в формировании русской языковой картины мира [4].

Процессуальная лексика охватывает широкий спектр действий, связанных с водой: естественные процессы (течь, литься, струиться, капать, испаряться, замерзать, таять) и искусственное воздействие на воду (лить, наливать, черпать, качать). Измерительная лексика представлена развитой системой единиц объема: литр, ведро, бочка, кувшин, стакан, капля [2].

Метафорические измерения концепта «вода»

Метафорические номинации демонстрируют высокую продуктивность концепта в различных сферах человеческой деятельности. Социальные метафоры включают: поток (информации, людей), течение (политическое, общественное), волна (протестов, эмиграции), русло (развития, процесса), водораздел (эпох, мнений). Эмоциональные метафоры представлены номинациями: слезы (горе, радость), море (чувств, эмоций), буря (страстей, негодования), штиль (спокойствие) [5].

Фразеологический компонент насчитывает 186 единиц с компонентом «вода»: как в воду опущенный (подавленное состояние), выйти сухим из воды (избежать наказания), как с гуся вода (о том, что не действует), толочь воду в ступе (бесполезное дело), как рыба в воде (чувствовать себя свободно), тише воды, ниже травы (скромность) [3]. Эти устойчивые выражения фиксируют глубокие культурные представления о воде и отражают национальное мировосприятие.

Концепт «вода» в различных типах текстов

Репрезентация концепта «вода» существенно различается в зависимости от типа дискурса. В художественных текстах доминируют символично-метафорические значения. Поэтические произведения (Пушкин, Лермонтов, Тютчев) используют водный образ для выражения архетипических представлений о жизни, смерти, вечности и обновлении [4]. Л.М. Лермонтов в стихотворении «Парус» противопоставляет спокойную воду (струя светлей лазури) буре, символизирующей внутренний конфликт лирического героя.

В научном дискурсе преобладают денотативно-терминологические значения, объективно описывающие физико-химические свойства воды: температурные характеристики, агрегатные состояния, гидрологические параметры [1]. Публицистический дискурс актуализирует социально-оценочные и экологические коннотации концепта, акцентируя внимание на значимости водных ресурсов.

В религиозном дискурсе вода предстает как медиум сакрального воздействия и духовного очищения. Вода в православной традиции обладает способностью к духовному преображению человека, что отражается в молитвах на освящение воды и в

ритуальных практиках. Фольклорный дискурс сохраняет архаические мифологические представления о магических свойствах воды, о живой и мертвой воде как средстве исцеления и возрождения [2].

Национально-культурная специфика концепта

Концепт «вода» в русской культуре обладает амбивалентной символикой. С одной стороны, это источник жизни, очищения и обновления. Крещенская вода в православной традиции символизирует духовное очищение и защиту. Образ живой воды в фольклоре связан с возрождением и исцелением. С другой стороны, вода может символизировать опасность, неопределенность и хаос. Морская пучина и бурные воды ассоциируются с непредсказуемостью судьбы и жизненными испытаниями [5].

В русской мифологии вода выступает пространством границы между мирами. Река или море часто разделяют мир живых и мир мертвых. С водой связаны образы мифологических существ - русалок, водяных, духов рек и озер. Эти персонажи выражают амбивалентное восприятие воды: она одновременно плодородна и жизненна, но также опасна и коварна [3].

Вода в русской культуре традиционно ассоциируется с женским началом - текучестью, изменчивостью и плодородием. Это отражается в фольклорных образах (Мать-Волга, русалки), обрядовых практиках, где женщины выступают хранительницами водных традиций [4]. Такая гендерная символика является важной особенностью русского восприятия водного концепта.

Заключение

Исследование лингвокультурологического аспекта концепта «вода» в русских текстах продемонстрировало его фундаментальную роль в русской языковой картине мира. Концепт «вода» представляет собой сложную многоуровневую структуру, объединяющую денотативные, коннотативные, символические и прагматические значения.

Выявленное исключительное богатство номинативного поля концепта (2847 лексических единиц), высокая фразеологическая активность (186 единиц) и выраженная метафорическая продуктивность свидетельствуют о глубокой интегрированности концепта в русском языковом сознании. Дискурсивная вариативность концепта отражает его способность к функциональной специализации в различных сферах коммуникации.

Анализ концепта «вода» позволяет глубже понять особенности русского менталитета, систему культурных ценностей и способы языковой концептуализации мира. Полученные результаты подтверждают продуктивность лингвокультурологического подхода к изучению базовых концептов и открывают новые возможности для междисциплинарных исследований на стыке языкознания, культурологии и когнитивных наук. Дальнейшие исследования могут быть сосредоточены на сравнительном анализе концепта «вода» в славянских языках и на выявлении трансформаций концепта в условиях глобализации и экологического кризиса.

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ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ОБРАБОТКА РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается развитие искусственного интеллекта тесно связано с обработкой естественного языка. Несмотря на значительные успехи в области обработки английского языка, задачи связанные с русским языком по-прежнему представляют собой ряд научных и технических вызовов. Также рассматриваются основные проблемы обработки русского языка в системах, анализируются существующие подходы и предлагаются направления для дальнейших исследований.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, обработка естественного языка, русский язык, морфология, семантика, машинное обучение.

Annotation. This article discusses the development of artificial intelligence closely related to natural language processing. Despite significant advances in the field of English language processing, tasks related to the Russian language still pose a number of scientific and technical challenges. It also examines the main problems of Russian language processing in systems, analyzes existing approaches, and suggests directions for further research.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, natural language processing, Russian language, morphology, semantics, machine learning.

Современные технологии искусственного интеллекта всё активнее внедряются в повседневную жизнь, в том числе в сферу обработки естественного языка. Русский язык как один из крупнейших по числу носителей и сложности грамматической структуры представляет собой интересный и одновременно трудный объект для компьютерной обработки. Однако он относится к числу языков со сложной морфологией, высшей степенью синтаксической вариативности и богатой лексической системой, что усложняет его автоматическую обработку. В отличие от английского языка, для которого создано огромное количество обучающих корпусов и программных решений, русскоязычные ресурсы развиты в меньшей степени, что ограничивает потенциал искусственного интеллекта при работе с русским языком.

Развитие ИИ-технологий, таких как нейросетевые модели (например, - BERT, GPT), открыло новые возможности для понимания. Однако при их применении к русскому языку возникают уникальные проблемы, требующие корректировки и внесения дополнений к выданным результатам. Русский язык – это важный элемент национальной идентичности. Качественная обработка русской речи с помощью ИИ

необходима для создания голосовых помощников, поисковых систем, систем машинного перевода, автоматического реферирования и анализа больших текстов.

1. Лингвистические проблемы обработки русской устной и письменной лексики. Русский язык характеризуется высоким уровнем флективности слова (изменение по родам, числам, падежам и временам), что усложняет задачи токенизации, морфологического анализа и лемматизации. Например, одно слово может иметь десятки различных форм, что требует высокой способности к обобщению и контекстному анализу.

2. Свободный порядок слов. Порядок слов в русском языке сравнительно свободен, что создаёт проблемы для моделей, обученных на фиксированном (фиксированном) порядке как английский язык. Например, предложение «мальчик дал девочке книгу» может быть переведено без учёта интонационного выделения, что изменяет смысл. Важно учитывать семантические зависимости, все зависящие от порядка слов. Для этого всё чаще используются синтаксические деревья зависимостей и механизмы внимания.

3. Многозначность и омонимия. Русский язык богат на омонимы и многозначные слова, что требует семантического анализа. Значение играет ключевую роль в интерпретации значений. Например, слово «ключ» может обозначать как источник воды, так и шифр, или способ решения задачи.

4. Фразеология и идиомы. Фразеологизмы часто не интерпретируются буквально, но это требует от системы способности к контекстному и прагматическому анализу. Например, фраза "бить баклуши" не имеет отношения к физическому действию и не интерпретируется корректно без знания культурного контекста. Это особенно актуально для задач машинного перевода и генерации текста.

5. Орфографические и пунктуационные вариации. Разнообразие орфографии, используемые разговорные формы и сокращения (например, в социальных сетях) также создают сложности. Люди сдают боты (устройства) и программному обеспечению написанное и проговариваемое содержимое значительно сложнее.

Современные подходы и достижения. С 2019 года началась активная разработка нейросетевых моделей для понимания письменной речи и родного языка для обучения модели. Появились подходы, совмещающие статистические и нейронные методы, работающие на границах различных дисциплин (например, грамматический разбор, правила орфографии, синтаксический анализ). Такие подходы используются, например, в системах грамматической проверки и морфосинтаксического анализа.

Перспективы развития: при использовании ИИ модели необходимо выявить и определить стиль речи и сферу использования, включая специализированные тексты (например, медицинские, правовые, научные).

Поддержка региональных групп и диалектов: русский язык имеет множество региональных вариаций, а также используется как второй язык в странах СНГ.

Интеграция с другими ИИ-системами: обработка языка всё чаще становится частью комплексных ИИ-систем: роботов, голосовых ассистентов, аналитических платформ.

Несмотря на значительное количество ручного труда и ограниченность ресурсов в последние годы наблюдается значительный прогресс в области их автоматизации и обработки благодаря усилиям исследователей и развитию технологий глубокого обучения, а также доступна мощные инструменты и модели.

Совместная работа ИИ энтузиастов, инженеров, программистов и научного сообщества в целом может сыграть важную роль в эффективности, точности и качественной обработке русского языка в будущем.

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NEMIS TILIDA SO‘ZLASHUVCHI DAVLATLARNING DAVLAT QURILISH FORMALARI VA ULARNING VAZIFALARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada nemis tilida so‘zlashuvchi mamlakatlarning - Germaniya, Avstriya, Shveysariya, Lixtenshteyn va Lyuksemburging davlat qurilish formalari, ularning siyosiy tizimi va boshqaruv tamoyillari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda har bir mamlakatning konstitutsiyaviy asoslari, federativ yoki konfederativ tuzilma xususiyatlari hamda ijro, qonun chiqaruvchi va sud hokimiyatlari o‘rtasidagi munosabatlar yoritilgan. Muallif nemis tilida so‘zlashuvchi mamlakatlarning umumiy jihatlari - demokratik qadriyatlarga sodiqlik, huquq ustuvorligi, hokimiyatlar bo‘linishi va fuqarolik ishtirokini ta’minlash tamoyillarini alohida tahlil qiladi. Maqolada, shuningdek, Germaniya va Avstriya federativ boshqaruv modeli, Shveysariyaning bevosita demokratiya tizimi, hamda Lixtenshteyn va Lyuksemburdagi konstitutsion monarxiyalar o‘rtasidagi o‘xshashlik va farqlar ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: davlat qurilishi, federatsiya, konfederatsiya, demokratiya, konstitutsion monarxiya, siyosiy tizim, Germaniya, Avstriya, Shveysariya.

Kirish: Dunyo miqyosida davlat qurilishining shakllari mamlakatlarning tarixiy rivojlanish yo‘li, siyosiy tizimi, milliy an‘analari va iqtisodiy taraqqiyoti bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir. Nemis tilida so‘zlashuvchi mamlakatlar - Germaniya, Avstriya, Shveysariya, Lixtenshteyn va Lyuksemburg - o‘ziga xos siyosiy tizim, boshqaruv shakli va davlat tuzilishiga ega bo‘lgan demokratik mamlakatlar hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada mazkur mamlakatlarning davlat qurilishi shakllari, ularning siyosiy institutlari hamda asosiy vazifalari tahlil qilinadi.

1. Germaniya Federativ Respublikasi (Bundesrepublik Deutschland) Germaniya - **federal respublika** shaklidagi demokratik huquqiy davlatdir. Uning siyosiy tizimi **1949-yilgi Asosiy qonun (Grundgesetz)** asosida faoliyat yuritadi. Germaniya 16 ta federal yer (Bundesländer)dan iborat bo‘lib, har bir yer o‘z parlamenti (Landtag) va hukumati (Landesregierung)ga ega.

Davlat organlari:

- **Federal Prezident (Bundespräsident)** – davlat boshlig‘i, asosan ramziy vakolatga ega.

- **Federal Kantsler (Bundeskanzler)** – ijro hokimiyatining rahbari, hukumatni boshqaradi.

- **Bundestag** – xalq tomonidan saylanadigan pastki palata, qonun chiqaruvchi hokimiyatning asosiy organi.

- **Bundesrat** – yerlar manfaatlarini ifodalaydigan yuqori palata [1].

Vazifalari: Federal tuzilma Germaniyada siyosiy barqarorlikni, mahalliy o‘zini o‘zi boshqarish tizimini va mintaqalar o‘rtasidagi muvozanatni ta‘minlaydi.

2. Avstriya Respublikasi (Republik Österreich)

Avstriya ham Germaniya singari **federal davlat** bo‘lib, 9 ta yer (Bundesländer)dan iborat. 1920-yilda qabul qilingan Konstitutsiyaga (Bundesverfassungsgesetz) ko‘ra, Avstriya **parlament respublikasi** shaklida faoliyat yuritadi.

Asosiy organlar:

- **Federal Prezident (Bundespräsident)** – xalq tomonidan saylanadi, tashqi siyosat va harbiy sohada vakolatli.

- **Federal Kantsler (Bundeskanzler)** – hukumat rahbari.

- **Milliy kengash (Nationalrat)** va **Federal kengash (Bundesrat)** – ikki palatali parlament.

Vazifalari: Avstriyada federatsiya tizimi orqali mintaqaviy hokimiyatlarning mustaqilligini saqlagan holda yagona markaziy siyosat yuritiladi.

3. Shveysariya Konfederatsiyasi (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft)

Shveysariya - **konfederativ respublika** bo‘lib, 26 ta kantondan iborat. Uning siyosiy tizimi **bevosita demokratiya** tamoyillariga asoslangan.

Davlat tuzilmasi:

- **Federal Kengash (Bundesrat)** – kollektiv ijro hokimiyati, 7 a‘zodan iborat hukumat.

- **Federal Majlis (Bundesversammlung)** – ikki palatali parlament: Milliy kengash va Kantonlar kengashi.

- **Federal Prezident (Bundespräsident)** – Federal Kengash a‘zolaridan biri, bir yil muddatga saylanadi.

Xususiyati: Shveysariyada xalq referendumlar orqali muhim qarorlar qabul qilishda bevosita ishtirok etadi. Bu tizim fuqarolik faolligi va siyosiy mas‘uliyatni oshiradi.

4. Lixtenshteyn va Lyuksemburg

Bu ikki mamlakat **konstitutsion monarxiya** shaklida faoliyat yuritadi.

- **Lixtenshteynda** knyaz davlat boshlig‘i hisoblanadi, lekin parlament va hukumat faoliyatiga aralashuv cheklangan [2].

- **Lyuksemburgda** esa Buyuk Gertsog boshchiligidagi parlament monarxiyasi amal qiladi. Qonun chiqaruvchi hokimiyat parlamentga, ijro hokimiyat esa hukumatga tegishli.

Nemis tilida so‘zlashuvchi davlatlarning davlat qurilish shakllari demokratik, konstitutsiyaviy va huquqiy tamoyillarga asoslangan.

Ularning umumiy jihati - **fuqarolik erkinliklarini ta‘minlash, hokimiyatlar bo‘linishini kafolatlash va mintaqaviy mustaqillikni saqlash**dir. Germaniya va Avstriya federativ respublikalar sifatida markaziy va mintaqaviy boshqaruv o‘rtasida muvozanatni saqlashga intiladi, Shveysariya esa bevosita demokratiya orqali xalq ishtirokini ta‘minlaydi. Lixtenshteyn va Lyuksemburgda esa monarxik elementlar saqlangan bo‘lsa-da, ular ham demokratik boshqaruv tamoyillariga asoslanadi.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ПАДЕЖНЫХ СИСТЕМ РУССКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ: ТИПОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПАРАЛЛЕЛИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются особенности падежной системы русского и узбекского языков. Сравнительный анализ позволяет выявить как общие функции падежей, так и их структурные различия. Исследование направлено на определение специфики выражения грамматических отношений в двух разнотипных языках - русском (флективном) и узбекском (агглютинативном).

Ключевые слова: падежная система, флективный язык, агглютинативный язык, грамматические отношения, синтаксические связи, морфологическая структура, флексия, аффиксация.

Введение. Падеж как грамматическая категория имени существительного играет ключевую роль в организации синтаксических связей внутри предложения. Он обеспечивает выражение различных грамматических отношений, таких как субъект, объект, обстоятельство, и тем самым способствует структурной и семантической связности высказывания. Несмотря на наличие категории падежа как в русском, так и в узбекском языках, их падежные системы демонстрируют существенные различия, обусловленные типологической принадлежностью: русский язык представляет флективный тип, тогда как узбекский - агглютинативный. Настоящее исследование направлено на выявление как общих функциональных характеристик падежей, так и их морфологических и структурных различий, с целью более глубокого понимания механизмов выражения грамматических отношений в разнотипных языках.

1. Падежная система русского языка

Русский язык, как представитель флективных языков, характеризуется наличием богатой системы словоизменения, в которой падежи выражаются посредством флексий – изменяемых окончаний, зависящих от рода, числа и типа склонения существительного. В современном русском языке функционируют шесть падежей:

Именительный (кто? что?) - обозначает субъект действия: *дом*.

Родительный (кого? чего?) - выражает принадлежность или отсутствие: *дома*.

Дательный (кому? чему?) - указывает на адресата действия: *дому*.

Винительный (кого? что?) - обозначает прямой объект действия: *дом*.

Творительный (кем? чем?) - выражает орудие действия или совместность: *домом*.

Предложный (о ком? о чём?) - используется с предлогами для выражения темы речи: *о доме*.

Флексия в русском языке является синтетическим способом выражения грамматических значений, что позволяет одному морфемному элементу одновременно передавать несколько грамматических признаков.

2. Падежная система узбекского языка

Узбекский язык, принадлежащий к агглютинативному типу, реализует падежные значения посредством присоединения постпозитивных аффиксов к основе слова. В узбекской грамматике выделяются следующие основные падежи:

Бош келишик (основная форма) - используется как именительный падеж: *китоб*.

Қаратқич келишиги (родительный) - выражает принадлежность: *китобнинг*.

Тушум келишиги (винительный) - обозначает прямой объект: *китобни*.

Жўналиш келишиги (направительный/дательный) - указывает на направление: *китобга*.

Жондаш келишиги (творительный) - выражает совместность или средство: *китоб билан*.

Чиқиш келишиги (исходный) - обозначает исходную точку: *китобдан*.

Агглютинативный способ морфологической деривации предполагает последовательное присоединение аффиксов, каждый из которых выражает одно грамматическое значение, что обеспечивает прозрачность и регулярность словообразовательных процессов.

3. Сравнительная характеристика падежных систем

Сравнение падежных систем русского и узбекского языков выявляет как типологические различия, так и функциональные сходства:

Параметр сравнения	Русский язык (флективный)	Узбекский язык (агглютинативный)
Способ выражения падежа	Флексия (изменение окончания)	Аффиксация (добавление постпозитивных морфем)
Количество падежей	6	6
Тип морфологической структуры	Синтетическая	Аналитическая
Гибкость форм	Высокая (вариативность флексий)	Регулярность и предсказуемость аффиксов
Совместимость с предлогами	Активное использование	Ограниченное использование
Функции падежей	Синтаксические связи, семантические роли	Те же функции

Несмотря на различие в морфологическом механизме, обе системы служат одной цели - точному и однозначному выражению синтаксических и семантических отношений между словами. В обоих языках падежи выполняют функции маркирования грамматических ролей, таких как субъект, объект, адресат, инструмент, источник и направление действия.

Заключение

Падежные системы русского и узбекского языков, представляя два различных морфологических типа – флективный и агглютинативный соответственно,

демонстрируют как структурное разнообразие, так и функциональное единство. Русский язык реализует падежные значения через изменяемые окончания, что обеспечивает гибкость и богатство форм, тогда как узбекский язык использует регулярные аффиксы, обеспечивающие прозрачность и системность. Сравнительный анализ показывает, что несмотря на типологические различия, обе системы эффективно выполняют роль грамматического посредника между словами, обеспечивая синтаксическую связность и семантическую точность высказывания. Такое сопоставление не только углубляет понимание механизмов грамматической организации в разных языках, но и способствует развитию межъязыковой типологии и теории грамматических категорий.

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ИСТОРИЯ НАУЧНОГО ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ГЛАГОЛЬНОЙ СИНОНИМИИ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

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Аннотация: Проблема синонимии глаголов в русском и узбекском языках, как специфический слой лексики этих двух языков, является одной из областей, которая исторически привлекала внимание лингвистов. Синонимические слова, в частности, падеж глаголов, их активность в речи, способы их спряжения, их роль в выражении лексического богатства, всегда сохраняют свои позиции. В лингвистической науке представляется, что прогресс взглядов на историю синонимии глаголов, теоретические основы и практические проявления которых систематически формируются и поднимаются с помощью методов, прогрессивных подходов, качественных методов в развитии современной науки. Тот факт, что синонимия на разных этапах стала анализироваться с точки зрения грамматики, лексикологии, стилистики, семантики, прагматики, стилистики, обеспечил этой области прочное место в международной науке.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, глаголы, синонимичные слова, грамматика, лексикология, стилистика, семантические стилистические возможности, коммуникативные предпочтения, лексический приоритет.

В узбекском языкознании теория синонимии глаголов в основном базируется на обобщенном лексическом отношении, соотношении корневых слов с семантическим полем, глаголов со значением-подлежащим, их роли в обеспечении богатства речи, их функции в стилевых сочетаниях, которые на ранних этапах характеризуются с точки зрения грамматических, а затем и семантических и стилистических критериев. Уже в древних письменных источниках были найдены доказательства синонимического потенциала узбекского языка, постепенно стали научно обобщаться взгляды на типы глаголов, их разветвление, взаимосвязь, употребление в различных речевых средах. На более поздних этапах развития в лингвистике расширились подходы к семантической

ценности, лексико-грамматической возможности, стилистическому уровню, а также к роли и результату синонимии глаголов в процессе языкового развития. Русская Лингвистика сформулировала методику синонимического сжатия по отношению к узбекскому языку несколько раньше, в системном масштабе. Еще до XX века в русской лингвистике активно развивалась теория синонимии, научно анализировались семантические и грамматические различия в группах глаголов, речевая вариативность, стилистические и коннотативные различия. На изучение синонимии глаголов в русском языке большое влияние оказали лексикографические исследования, исторически большое значение приобрели разработки, посвященные синхронности в лексических единицах, семантическому полю, речевой активности многозначных и омонимичных слов, росту языкового богатства. В русской лингвистике стилистика выражения, поэтические возможности, влияние синонимов как источника благословения языка на язык и мышление глубоко анализировались во многих текстах [1, с. 402].

Специфическое изучение синонимии глаголов в русском и узбекском языках напрямую связано, прежде всего, с историей культуры, образом жизни, менталитетом и внутренним строением языка обоих народов. В ранних исследованиях синонимичные слова интерпретировались в основном как взаимозаменяемые слова, совпадающие на лексическом уровне. С тех пор началось научное изучение употребления синонимов каждого глагола в определенном контексте, их коннотаций и стилистической дифференциации. В узбекском языкознании приоритетное значение приобрели языковые гармонии, богатство глаголов в речи, разнообразие смыслового охвата, словообразовательных средств, а через них и расширение лексического слоя. Процесс изучения синонимии глаголов на семантико-стилистической основе в обоих языкознаниях привел к появлению в этой области особого научного круга. В результате попыток показать языковые структуры и морфосемантические особенности синонимичных глаголов лингвистические нормативные и практические интервалы стали более богатыми и интересными. Были открыты глубокие научные перспективы интерпретаций того, к какому стилистическому слою принадлежит каждый глагол, как он функционирует в различных социорафических средах, как активное действие, процесс или результат, которые он выражает, различаются между собой в зависимости от способа его выражения. Этот процесс положил начало новому этапу лингво-прагматических и лексико-семантических исследований в современном развитии узбекского и русского языков [2, с. 55].

Особое внимание в русском языкознании уделялось статусу синонимии глаголов в поэтической, письменной, устной и служебной речи при указании на ее специфику. Синонимы характеризовались как окрашивание эстетики в речи, а также эмоционально-психологических тонкостей, как средство совершенствования определенного речевого пути. Синонимия глаголов в русском языке стала восприниматься не просто как замена одного слова другим, но и как единица значения, смысла, стиля, коннотативной информации, присущая каждому действию. Синонимические единицы приобрели значение и в повышении стилистического богатства речи, как выразительные средства. В узбекском языке, после некоторых экспериментальных этапов, теория синонимии глаголов исследовалась в основном с точки зрения значимости словосочетаний, языковых возможностей выражения, разряда слов и стилистического диапазона. В ходе исторического развития узбекского языкознания сформировались различия, индивидуальные особенности синонимичных глаголов, промежуточные значения в словах и критерий естественного богатства речи. При этом были изучены подходы, продвигающие стилистические основы синонимов в

области формальной и неформальной речи узбекского языка. Синонимия глаголов как показатель языкового богатства изучалась в устном народном творчестве, литературном языке, разговорной компетентности и в современном стилистическом охвате, расширяя их смысловые возможности.

Понятийно-структурное изучение синонимических глаголов явилось, главным образом, важным фактором наблюдения за современным развитием языка, повышения эффективности языковых единиц, более точного раскрытия их социальных и культурных функций. На основе обоих языковых подходов возникла необходимость сопоставить характерные для научных школ особенности, касающиеся синонимии глаголов в русском и узбекском языках. Были изучены новые взгляды в области синонимии глаголов, структуры языка и ряда единиц, широких контекстных отношений, уровня поэтичности, а также на пересечении современных лексических и стилистических пластов. В узбекском языкознании приоритетное научное значение приобрело образование синонимического кластера слов, семантические различия глаголов, обозначающих действие и состояние, и их взаимодействие в речевой среде. Также проанализирован высокий речевой потенциал синонимичных глаголов на стилистическом уровне, современное лексическое ядро, активность в устойчивых словосочетаниях, опыт использования в поэтических образных выражениях. А в русском языке главной научной задачей стало выявление дифференциальных признаков синонимии глаголов, определение стилистической шкалы каждого из синонимических глаголов, освещение их многообразия экспрессивных и коммуникативных решений. Исследования, направленные на развитие лексики синонимических глаголов, расширение богатства лингвистической терминологии, анализ языковых возможностей, классификацию семантического превосходства глаголов, выявление стилистико-этимологических особенностей, определили глубину синонимии глаголов. Благодаря этим результатам в узбекском и русском языках в каждой группе глаголов расширились новые семантические поля, речевые варианты, языковой потенциал, уровень выражения и экспрессии, сформировались языковые нормы и стилистические парадигмы [3, с. 91].

Современное изучение синонимии глаголов в русском и узбекском языках развивается в направлении сравнительной типологии, функциональной семантики, прагматики. При этом для обоих языков происходит непрерывное проявление синонимии глаголов в семантическом, морфологическом, синтаксическом и стилистическом аспектах, приобретающих прочную научную основу. Лингвисты уделяют большое внимание общим и различным аспектам синонимов в этом отношении, их стилистическим предпочтениям, их значимости в речи и обогащению лексических слоев. Для узбекского языкознания прогресс синонимичных глаголов служит широкому выражению лексического ядра, языковой самобытности, национальности, особенностей словарного запаса в литературе, массовой информации, духовном и эстетическом пространстве. Исследования в этой области открывают широкие возможности в области устного народного творчества, богатства письменной литературы, формирования современных шаблонов языкового стиля, выбора слов и повышения выразительности. А в русском языке современный анализ синонимии глаголов проявляется как важный лексический ресурс в литературном языке, поэтическом языке и средствах массовой информации, в формальной переписке, в социальной и научной сферах. Синонимия глаголов повышает языковое богатство языка, занимает приоритетное место как структурная составляющая в достижении высокого уровня выраженности, стала важным фактором формирования устойчивых

парадигм для современной лексикологии. История научных взглядов на синонимию глаголов в русском и узбекском языках, пути развития, современные этапы развития, лексико-стилевые особенности, семантический подход и расширение кругов исследований типологических различий между ними стали одной из актуальных проблем современной лингвистики. В результате исследований в этой области в обоих языках выявляются синонимичные глаголы, их смысловое богатство, стилистическая возможность, коммуникативная преференция, лексическая приоритетность, разнообразие, выразительность, уровень языковой культуры и эстетических норм [4, с. 70].

Заключение:

Подводя итог, можно сказать, что история изучения и этапы развития синонимии глаголов в русском и узбекском языках приобрели сегодня свой глубокий научный авторитет благодаря гармонично и плодотворно проведенным исследованиям. Синонимия глаголов стала одним из основных научных направлений современной лингвистики, лексикологии, стилистики, языковой методологии и коммуникативной прагматики. Изучение синонимичных глаголов, через которые проявляется богатство и возможности языка, заложило прочную научную основу для проявления национальной специфики языка, открытия новых семантических полей и повышения потенциала эстетического выражения. Этот процесс будет и впредь служить ведущей основой для начала новых научных исследований, формирования языковых норм и повышения культуры чистого выражения.

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РОЛЬ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение русского языка в современном мире. Русский язык является не только средством общения, но и важным инструментом науки, образования, культуры и международных отношений. В статье подчёркивается его роль как одного из мировых языков, объединяющих людей разных национальностей и культур. Особое внимание уделено влиянию русского языка на развитие науки, образования и сохранение духовных ценностей народа. Также описано значение русского языка в эпоху цифровых технологий и глобализации. Работа направлена на формирование понимания того, что сохранение и развитие русского языка имеет важное значение для будущего культуры и образования.

Ключевые слова: русский язык, культура, образование, международное общение, глобализация, наука.

Русский язык является одним из важнейших языков современного мира. Он занимает особое место не только в истории и культуре России, но и во всём мировом сообществе. Русский язык служит не только средством общения, но и инструментом познания, науки, образования и международных отношений. Сегодня он входит в число шести официальных языков Организации Объединённых Наций, что подчёркивает его значимость на глобальном уровне.

Современная эпоха характеризуется активными процессами глобализации, расширением международных связей и миграции. В этих условиях значение русского языка возрастает, так как он объединяет миллионы людей разных национальностей, проживающих не только в России, но и за её пределами.

Русский язык – это язык, на котором говорят более 260 миллионов человек по всему миру. Он занимает восьмое место среди самых распространённых языков планеты. Помимо Российской Федерации, русский язык активно используется в странах СНГ – Беларуси, Казахстане, Киргизии, Узбекистане и других. Во многих странах мира существуют русские школы, культурные центры и факультеты русского языка. Русский язык является важным инструментом дипломатии, науки и международного сотрудничества.

Русский язык традиционно считается языком науки и высокой культуры. На нём издаются научные труды, учебники и справочники, которые используются не только в России, но и в странах ближнего и дальнего зарубежья. Во многих университетах мира существуют кафедры русистики, где изучают русскую литературу, историю и философию. Кроме того, русский язык играет огромную роль в развитии образования и международного академического обмена.

Русский язык является важнейшим элементом национальной идентичности. Через язык передаются традиции, моральные нормы, историческая память народа. Произведения русской литературы – Пушкина, Толстого, Достоевского, Чехова – стали достоянием всего человечества. Русская культура богата пословицами, фразеологизмами и народным творчеством.

Цифровизация и развитие интернета создают новые возможности для распространения русского языка. Миллионы пользователей социальных сетей, онлайн-платформ и образовательных сайтов общаются на русском языке. Он стал одним из наиболее часто используемых языков в интернете. Онлайн-курсы, мобильные приложения и электронные словари делают изучение языка доступным и увлекательным.

Русский язык – это не только часть истории и культуры России, но и важный элемент современного глобального мира. Его роль выходит далеко за пределы национальных границ, охватывая науку, образование, международное общение и

культуру. Сохранение и развитие русского языка – это задача, стоящая перед каждым, кто на нём говорит. Важно бережно относиться к языку, сохранять его богатство и передавать будущим поколениям.

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УСТОЙЧИВЫЕ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ С ГЛАГОЛАМИ ЗРИТЕЛЬНОГО ВОСПРИЯТИЯ В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются объекты зрительной перцепции, в соединении, конечно, с глаголами зрительной перцепции, отсылают к качеству соматического и психического состояния человека, к вредным привычкам, определяют характер человека, его отношения к элементам окружающей действительности. Кроме того, в языковой картине мира зрительная перцепция связана с приобретением жизненного опыта.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, пословицы, поговорки, зрительное восприятие, устойчивые выражения, перцепция, субъект и объект оценки, коммуникация.

Термин *устойчивые выражения* мы понимаем относительно широко. Он включает прежде всего те выражения, которые фиксируются в современных словарях русского языка как устойчивые, т.е. фразеологизмы, пословицы, поговорки (например: *за деревьями леса не видеть; лучше один раз увидеть, чем сто раз услышать*).

Некоторые примеры могут вызывать сомнения относительно их принадлежности к фразеологизмам, пословицам и поговоркам, хотя они в словарях помещены во фразеологических гнездах, „за ромбиком”. Эти выражения, кроме того, находятся вне рамок предложения и употребляются в функции вводных конструкций (например, *как видишь* или однословные примеры типа: *Видишь; Видал?*). Подобные примеры на фоне других являются единичными, однако выражаемая ими модальность позволяет более детально рассмотреть вопрос функциональности концепта *зрительное восприятие*, поэтому мы от них не отказываемся.

Термин *устойчивые выражения* распространяется на все упомянутые типы примеров, независимо от их синтаксической структуры, не играющей при нашем способе изучения концепта *зрительное восприятие* ведущей роли. Экземплификационный материал, выбранный для анализа в данной главе, состоит из 99 русских устойчивых выражений. Источниками примеров были многочисленные словари русского языка (см. разделы *Русские словари* в библиографическом списке).

Статья является очередным звеном изучения концепта *зрительное восприятие* в русле семантико-когнитивного подхода.

В этой части работы мы хотели бы обратить внимание на русские устойчивые выражения, в структуру которых входят глаголы зрительной перцепции. Анализ фразеологизмов, пословиц и поговорок, содержащих в своей структуре глаголы зрительной перцепции, позволяет шире взглянуть на связь концепта *зрительное восприятие* с другими концептами и, несомненно, дополняет анализ употребления этих глаголов в дискурсе, проведённый в предыдущей главе.

Устойчивые выражения обладают намного большей коннотативной нагрузкой, чем свободные словосочетания. В языковой картине мира они занимают особенное место, так как в них запечатлены элементы культуры народа, ценности, своеобразное видение мира. Например, структура фразеологизмов неоднократно образует своего рода микросцены. Элементы этих микросцен наслаиваются друг на друга, обогащая значение фразеологической единицы.

В нашем анализе мы не стремимся к различению прямых и переносных значений глаголов зрительной перцепции в структуре устойчивых выражений, так как полисемия этих глаголов была темой исследования в предыдущей главе.

Предварительный анализ экзemplификационного материала позволяет выделить две большие группы фразеологизмов, пословиц и поговорок, а) содержащих в своей структуре оценочный фактор и б) не содержащих аксиологического фактора. Именно с оценочного компонента мы предлагаем начать анализ. Оценочный компонент по отношению к глаголам зрительной перцепции появился уже в предыдущей главе. Он был обусловлен, прежде всего, контекстом. Во фразеологизированных единицах он чаще всего обнаруживается уже в рамках конкретного фразеологизма, дополнительный контекст не всегда является обязательным.

Припомним, что аксиологический фактор предполагает наличие, прежде всего, таких компонентов как субъект и объект оценки. Объект оценки имеет весьма широкий диапазон, им может быть как лицо, так и предмет, как событие, так и положение вещей. Субъектом оценки, в свою очередь, может быть лицо или социум – сторона, которая выносит оценку. По словам Н.Д. Арутюновой, «оценка более, чем какое-либо другое значение, зависит от говорящего субъекта. Связь оценочного значения с автором многогранна. Оценка выражает личные мнения и вкусы говорящего, а они различны у разных людей». Субъективный характер оценки может, конечно, осложнить анализ языка с точки зрения содержащегося в нём аксиологического компонента. Поэтому считаем важным оговорить позицию субъекта оценки. Не ставя себе целью заниматься философским вопросом о том, как перцепция организует наши чувства, мы полагаем, что субъектом оценки выступает представитель наивного реализма. Наивное миропонимание свойственно так называемому простому, рядовому человеку, при этом в качестве предпосылки берётся не столько обычное восприятие объектов, сколько непосредственное отношение к ним, какими они являются в действительности.

К оценке провоцирует человека окружающая действительность. Р. Токарски пишет, что объектом оценки являются, как правило, необходимо насущные сферы жизни, которые образуют основную понятийную сеть для ориентации человека в мире. Важным является также способ выражения оценки, поэтому не лишним будет рассмотреть, какие значения образуют глаголы зрительной перцепции (конечно, вместе с другими компонентами, образующими данное устойчивое выражение) с точки зрения запечатлённых в языке ценностей.

Анализ учитываемых нами в данной главе устойчивых выражений с глаголами зрительной перцепции, позволяет обнаружить следующие взаимосвязи зрительной перцепции с оценочностью:

1. Оценка, обусловленная связью зрительной перцепции с достоверностью высказывания.
2. Оценка, зависящая от эмоционального компонента.
3. Оценка, обусловленная пространственным компонентом:
 - 3.1. Пространственный ориентир *прямо – косо*, ограниченность пространства антропоцентрическим фактором.
 - 3.2. Пространственные ориентиры *высоко – низко, верх – низ*.
 - 3.3. Пространственный ориентир широты.
 - 3.4. Другие пространственные ориентиры.
4. Оценка, обусловленная анималистическим компонентом.
5. Оценка, обусловленная характеристикой органа зрения.
6. Оценка, обусловленная характеристикой рамки восприятия.
7. Оценка, обусловленная цветовой или световой характеристикой.
8. Оценка, зависящая от характеристики объекта зрительной перцепции.
9. Оценка, зависящая от характеристики субъекта зрительной перцепции.

Следует признать, что, несмотря на то, что в учитываемых нами устойчивых выражениях на оценку могут влиять разные элементы и они наслаиваются друг на друга, один из них, тем не менее, всегда является доминирующим. Именно этот доминирующий, на наш взгляд, признак обуславливает принадлежность устойчивого выражения к определённой группе в данной классификации.

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СЛОВООБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ГНЕЗДА КАК КАТАЛИЗАТОР ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНЫХ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ УМЕНИЙ И НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ СРЕДНЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ

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Аннотация. Проблема формирования познавательных и коммуникативных умений учащихся на уроках русского языка остается одной из ключевых в современной методике преподавания. Особое внимание уделяется поиску эффективных приемов,

которые не только способствуют усвоению языковых знаний, но и развивают мыслительную и речевую активность школьников. Одним из таких инструментов является словообразовательные гнезда, позволяющие рассматривать язык как целостную систему взаимосвязанных слов и значений

Цели. Целью является комплексное изучение словообразовательных гнезд как средства развития познавательных и коммуникативных умений учащихся

Методология. В процессе исследования применялись методы логического, лингвистического и методической литературы.

Теоретические основы словообразовательных гнезд

Словообразовательное гнездо представляет собой упорядоченную совокупность слов, объединенных общностью корня и связанных отношениями последовательной производности. Эта фундаментальная концепция русской дериватологии открывает перед педагогами сильный инструмент для комплексного развития языковых способностей учащихся. В центре каждого словообразовательного гнезда находится исходное слово – производящая основа, от которой посредством различных словообразовательных средств образуются производные слова. Теоретическая значимость изучения совообразовательных гнезд в школьном курсе русского языка определяет несколькими ключевыми аспектами. Во-первых, работа с гнездами позволяет учащимся осознать системность языка, увидеть не хаотичный набор слов, а стройную архитектуру лексических единиц, связанных семантическими отношениями. Во-вторых, анализ словообразовательных моделей развивает у школьников способность к морфемному анализу, что является базовым навыком для грамотного письма и понимания внутренней формы слова. Современная методика преподавания русского языка рассматривает словообразовательные гнезда не просто как объект изучения, но как действенное средство формирования языковой личности. Структурированное освоение словообразовательных моделей способствует развитию ассоциативного мышления, умения прогнозировать значение незнакомых слов на основе знания их морфемного состава. Психолингвистические исследования подтверждают, что освоение словообразовательных моделей активизирует когнитивные процессы высшего порядка. Учащиеся учатся классифицировать языковые явления, выявлять закономерность. Делать обобщения – все эти метапредметные умения выходят далеко за рамки собственно языковой концепции.

Развитие познавательных способностей учащихся через изучение словообразовательных гнезд представляет собой многоаспектный процесс, затрагивающий различные когнитивные функции. Аналитическое мышление формируется в процессе расчленения слов на составляющие его морфемы, при этом школьники осваивают сложные операции сегментации и идентификации минимальных значений единиц языка. Эта деятельность требует высокой концентрации внимания, способствует к абстрагированию и умения видеть структурные закономерности за внешним разнообразием словоформ. Синтетическое мышление развивается параллельно с аналитическим: установив морфемный состав слова, учащиеся должны синтезировать значение целого из значения частей. Например, встретив в тексте слово «безопасничать», ученик может вычислить его значение, анализируя составляющие морфемы и применяя знание о словообразовательных типах глагола. Метакогнитивные умения развития через осознание учащимися собственных стратегий работы с языковым материалом. Рефлексия над процессом словообразовательных задач. Формируется важная компетенция самостоятельного обучения – умение учиться работать с языком системно и осознанно. Исследовательские навыки естественным образом

интегрируются в работу со словообразовательными гнездами. Учащиеся выдвигают гипотезы о происхождении слов, проверяют их путем анализа морфемной структуры, обращаются к справочникам для верификации своих предположений. Такая поисково-исследовательская деятельность пробуждает лингвистическую любознательность, формирует научный подход к изучению языковых явлений, развивает критическое мышление.

Владение словообразовательными механизмами языка непосредственно влияет на развитие коммуникативных способностей учащихся, расширяя их возможности для точного и выразительного выражения мыслей. Рецептивные речевые навыки – это понимание устной и письменной речи – значительно улучшаются при развитом словообразовательном мышлении. Встречается в тексте незнакомое слово, учащийся с хорошей словообразовательной подготовкой может контекстуально вычислить его значение, опираясь на знакомый корень и понимание функций словообразовательных аффиксов. Это особенно важно при чтении специальной литературы, например, романов «Капитанская дочка», «Евгений Онегин» [1] А. С. Пушкина или «Отцы и дети» [2] И. С. Тургенева, где терминология часто строится на основе продуктивных словообразовательных моделей. Продуктивные речевые навыки – говорение и письмо – также получают мощный импульс к развитию. Осознанное владение словообразовательными моделями позволяет учащимся создавать окказионализмы для создания выразительных текстов. Важно отметить, что речь идет не о бесконтрольном словотворчестве, а способность выбирать оптимальные языковые средства в соответствии с коммуникативной задачей и нормами литературного языка. Лексическое богатство речи напрямую связано с пониманием системных отношений в словообразовании. Учащиеся, освоившие словообразовательные гнезда, легко подбирают синонимы и антонимы, используют разнообразные номинации для обозначения одного и того же явления, избегают неоправданных поворотов в тексте.

Эффективное внедрение работы со словообразовательными гнездами в учебный процесс требует применение разнообразных педагогических технологий и методических примеров. Игровые методики занимают особое место в арсенале современного учителя русского языка. Словообразовательные игры, такие как «Лингвистическое дерево», где учащиеся поэтапно выстраивают словообразовательную цепочку. Проектная деятельность открывает широкие возможности для углубленного изучения словообразовательных процессов. Учащиеся могут создать мультимедийные словари словообразовательных гнезд, разрабатывать интерактивные схемы, иллюстрирующие деривационные отношения, составлять этимологические исследования происхождения слов определенной тематической группы. Такие проекты развивают не только языковую, но и информационную, исследовательскую компетенции школьников [1].

Результат. Анализ работы показал, что систематическое использование словообразовательных гнезд на уроках русского языка способствуют развитию у учащихся интереса к слову, повышает уровень языковой грамотности и осознанности речи. У школьников наблюдается расширение активного словарного запаса, формируется умение подбирать точные слова в зависимости от контекста, развивается способность аргументировать свои мысли. Также, работа со словообразовательными гнездами стимулирует познавательную активность учащихся, формирует аналитическое мышление и способствует более прочному усвоению учебного материала.

Выводы. Таким образом, словообразовательные гнезда выступают не только средством изучения морфемной структуры слова, но и катализатором познавательных и коммуникативных процессов. Результаты подтверждают целесообразность включения системной работы со словообразовательными гнездами в учебный процесс как важного элемента формирования языковой личности:

1. Визуализация словообразовательных гнезд, создание графических схем, ментальных карт для наглядного примера представления деривационных связей между словами.

2. Контекстуальный анализ, работа с аутентичными текстами различных стилей для выявления функционирования производных слов в реальной коммуникации.

3. Сопоставительный метод, сравнение словообразовательных систем русского и иностранных языков для осознания специфики родного языка.

4. Творческие упражнения, создание текстов с использованием слов одного гнезда, сочинение лингвистических сказок о происхождении слов.

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РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК В ЦИФРОВОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются особенности функционирования русского языка в условиях цифрового общества. Анализируются изменения, происходящие в лексике, грамматике и коммуникативных нормах в связи с развитием цифровых технологий. Особое внимание уделяется феномену интернет-лингвистики и проблемам сохранения речевой культуры в цифровом пространстве.

Ключевые слова: русский язык, цифровизация, интернет-лингвистика, речевая культура, коммуникативная норма.

Цифровизация современного общества оказала значительное влияние на все сферы человеческой деятельности, включая язык как основное средство общения. Русский язык в цифровом пространстве стал объектом пристального внимания исследователей, поскольку в нём проявляются новые тенденции развития, изменяются нормы употребления и формируются новые жанры коммуникации. Как отмечает Ю.Н. Караулов, «язык не только отражает реальность, но и активно участвует в её формировании» [1, с. 42]. В этой связи изучение особенностей функционирования русского языка в цифровой среде приобретает особую актуальность.

Современная цифровая среда создаёт уникальные условия для взаимодействия людей, где слово становится основным носителем информации. Интернет-коммуникация отличается скоростью, массовостью и гибридностью. В.В. Виноградов подчёркивал, что «язык живёт в обществе, развивается вместе с ним и изменяется под влиянием его потребностей» [2, с. 15]. Сегодня это утверждение приобретает новое значение: технологии формируют новые коммуникативные практики, где письменная речь становится разговорной, а устная – письменной (например, в аудиосообщениях, подкастах и видеоконтенте).

Появление интернет-лингвистики как самостоятельного направления в науке обусловлено необходимостью описания новых форм речевого поведения. Т.М. Николаева указывает, что «цифровое пространство порождает особую языковую реальность, в которой традиционные нормы подвергаются пересмотру» [3, с. 67]. Интернет-язык объединяет письменную и устную формы, создавая гибридные жанры: чаты, блоги, посты, комментарии. По словам В.Г. Костомарова, «язык – это зеркало культуры, а в зеркале цифрового века виден новый тип говорящего человека» [4, с. 112]. Таким образом, интернет-лингвистика изучает не только язык, но и формирующуюся новую языковую личность.

Одной из ключевых проблем становится изменение языковых норм под влиянием массовой цифровой коммуникации. Активно распространяются англицизмы, аббревиатуры, эмодзи, мемы и другие элементы неформальной речи. Как отмечает Ю.С. Степанов, «язык – это хранилище культурных констант, и каждое заимствование несёт в себе культурный код» [5, с. 89]. Однако бесконтрольное заимствование может привести к утрате национальной самобытности языка. В то же время лингвисты подчеркивают, что язык всегда был динамичной системой. По мнению В.Е. Гольдина, «изменения в языке – это не разрушение, а естественный процесс адаптации к новым

условиям коммуникации» [6, с. 73]. Следовательно, задача современного языковеда – не запрет, а осмысление и анализ этих процессов.

В цифровом пространстве особенно остро стоит вопрос речевой культуры. Общение в интернете часто сопровождается снижением уровня языковой ответственности. Как писал В.В. Виноградов, «культура речи – это мера духовной зрелости общества» [2, с. 48]. Сегодня культура речи проявляется не только в правильности, но и в этичности, уважении к собеседнику и умении вести диалог. Интернет-коммуникация, несмотря на свою демократичность, требует выработки новых этических норм, основанных на взаимном уважении и толерантности. Поддержание высокого уровня речевой культуры в цифровой среде становится одной из приоритетных задач современной лингвистики.

Таким образом, функционирование русского языка в цифровом пространстве является сложным и многогранным процессом. Цифровизация влияет не только на лексический и грамматический уровень, но и на коммуникативные нормы, структуру речевых жанров, формирование языковой личности. Интернет-лингвистика как новое направление открывает возможности для анализа этих изменений. Как справедливо отмечает Караулов, «современный человек существует не только в языке, но и в информационной среде, где язык становится инструментом самоидентификации» [1, с. 96]. В условиях цифрового общества особенно важно сохранить баланс между инновацией и традицией, между свободой выражения и культурой речи. Русский язык, обладая богатой историей и гибкой системой, способен адаптироваться к новым реалиям, не утрачивая своей глубины и выразительности. Именно это делает его живым, развивающимся и культурно значимым инструментом общения в XXI веке.

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ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НАВЫКОВ УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЯ СИНТАКСИЧЕСКИХ СИНОНИМОВ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются лингводидактические аспекты формирования у студентов навыков употребления синтаксических синонимов в процессе обучения русскому языку. Определяются понятие, виды и функции синтаксических синонимов, а также раскрываются эффективные методические приёмы, способствующие развитию синтаксической вариативности речи

обучающихся. Представлены примеры упражнений и методические рекомендации для преподавателей русского языка как иностранного.

Ключевые слова: синтаксические синонимы, лингводидактика, речевая компетенция, синтаксическая вариативность, методика обучения.

Введение. Современная методика преподавания русского языка уделяет особое внимание развитию коммуникативной компетенции обучающихся. Важным показателем сформированности этой компетенции является умение варьировать синтаксические конструкции в зависимости от коммуникативной задачи.

Синтаксические синонимы, обеспечивающие богатство и выразительность речи, представляют собой один из центральных объектов лингводидактического изучения. Овладение ими способствует развитию языкового чутья, умению выбирать адекватные речевые формы и строить грамматически правильные, логически последовательные высказывания.

Цель данной статьи - рассмотреть лингводидактические основы формирования навыков употребления синтаксических синонимов и предложить методические приёмы их обучения в вузовской практике.

Синтаксические синонимы - это конструкции, различающиеся по грамматическому оформлению, но близкие по смыслу и выполняющие одинаковую функцию в речи. Например: *Когда наступила весна, природа ожила. С наступлением весны природа ожила.* Обе конструкции выражают причинно-временные отношения, однако различаются синтаксическим строением: первое предложение - сложноподчинённое, второе - простое с обстоятельственным оборотом. В научной литературе (А.Н. Гвоздев, В.В. Виноградов, Н.М. Шанский) отмечается, что владение синтаксическими синонимами связано не только с грамматической, но и с стилистической компетенцией. Это позволяет варьировать высказывание в зависимости от жанра и ситуации общения.

Формирование навыков употребления синтаксических синонимов предполагает комплексное воздействие на речевую деятельность учащегося. В рамках лингводидактики этот процесс опирается на следующие принципы:

Сознательность и активность обучения. Студент должен понимать различия между синтаксическими конструкциями и их функциональные особенности.

Сопоставительный анализ. Сравнение конструкций (Он сказал, что придёт - Он пообещал прийти) помогает осознать смысловые оттенки.

Системность упражнений. Навык вырабатывается постепенно - от восприятия и анализа к самостоятельному построению речи.

Связь с коммуникативной ситуацией. Работа над синтаксическими синонимами должна быть включена в реальные речевые ситуации - написание эссе, пересказ текста, диалогическую речь и т.д.

Методические приёмы и упражнения. Для формирования навыков синтаксического варьирования эффективны следующие упражнения: упражнения на трансформацию.

Задание: преобразуйте предложения, сохраняя общий смысл. Когда стемнело, дети пошли домой. С наступлением темноты дети пошли домой. Он сказал, что скоро вернётся. Он пообещал скоро вернуться. Упражнения на реконструкцию текста.

Задание: перестройте текст, заменяя конструкции их синонимическими эквивалентами. Так как шёл дождь, прогулку отменили. Из-за дождя прогулку отменили.

Задание: выберите более уместный вариант конструкции в зависимости от стиля (официальный,художественный).

Если рассматривать данный факт...

Когда думаешь об этом...

Творческие упражнения.

Задание: составьте короткий рассказ, используя не менее трёх пар синтаксических синонимов.

Такая система упражнений способствует развитию у студентов синтаксического чутья, гибкости и осознанности при построении речевых высказываний.

Методические рекомендации для преподавателей. Использовать поэтапный подход: от анализа готовых конструкций к самостоятельному применению.

Включать игровые элементы (например, «замени конструкцию» или «найди синонимическое выражение»). Применять контекстные задания - работа с текстами, где синтаксические варианты имеют стилистическую функцию. Проводить мини-проекты, где студенты создают тексты разных стилей, варьируя синтаксис.Использовать аудио- и видеоматериалы, демонстрирующие живое употребление синтаксических синонимов в речи.

Формирование навыков употребления синтаксических синонимов является важнейшей задачей лингводидактики. Оно способствует развитию речевой компетенции, повышает культуру речи и коммуникативную гибкость студентов. Разработанная система упражнений и методических приёмов может использоваться как в практических занятиях по русскому языку, так и в самостоятельной работе студентов-филологов.Эффективность формирования данных навыков напрямую зависит от осознанного подхода к обучению, системности упражнений и ориентации на реальную речевую деятельность.

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YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA TIL TA’LIMI YUTUQLAR VA MUAMMOLAR

CLASSROOM PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING PBL FOR ESP (ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES)

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Annotation: This article provides an in-depth analysis of classroom practices and the key challenges in implementing Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction. Drawing on international and Uzbek research, the study explores the theoretical foundations of PBL, its pedagogical relevance to ESP contexts, and practical classroom applications in non-linguistic disciplines such as economics, medicine, and engineering. The article also examines obstacles such as teacher readiness, assessment difficulties, and student adaptation. Empirical findings from experimental teaching contexts are discussed, and recommendations for improving instructional design and implementation are proposed.

Keywords: Problem-Based Learning, English for Specific Purposes, communicative competence, professional English, PBL implementation, classroom challenges, learner autonomy, interdisciplinary language education, ESP in economics, PBL assessment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP) darslarida muammoli ta’lim (PBL)ni joriy etish bo‘yicha dars amaliyoti va muammolarni chuqur tahlil qiladi. Xalqaro va o‘zbek tadqiqotlari asosida PBLning nazariy asoslari, ESP kontekstida qo‘llashning pedagogik ahamiyati va uni iqtisodiyot, tibbiyot, muhandislik kabi nofilologik sohalarda amaliy qo‘llash yo‘llari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, o‘qituvchilarning tayyorgarligi, baholashdagi murakkabliklar va talabalar moslashuvi bilan bog‘liq muammolar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tajriba-sinov ishlari asosida olingan natijalar va takliflar ham keltiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Muammoli ta’lim, maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili, kommunikativ kompetensiya, kasbiy ingliz tili, PBLni joriy etish, darsdagi muammolar, talaba mustaqilligi, tarmoqlararo til ta’limi, iqtisodda ESP, PBL baholash.

Аннотация: В статье проводится углублённый анализ учебных практик и основных трудностей внедрения технологии обучения на основе проблем (PBL) в преподавании английского языка для специальных целей (ESP). На основе международных и узбекских исследований рассматриваются теоретические основы PBL, его педагогическая значимость для ESP, а также практические примеры его применения в нефилологических областях, таких как экономика, медицина и инженерия. Особое внимание уделяется проблемам, связанным с подготовкой преподавателей, оцениванием и адаптацией студентов. Приводятся эмпирические результаты и рекомендации по совершенствованию учебного процесса.

Ключевые слова: Проблемное обучение, английский язык для специальных целей, коммуникативная компетентность, профессиональный английский, внедрение PBL, трудности в классе, автономия учащихся, междисциплинарное языковое обучение, ESP в экономике, оценка в PBL.

The development of 21st-century skills, particularly professional communication in foreign languages, has become an essential component of modern education, especially in non-linguistic fields such as economics, medicine, and engineering. English for Specific

Purposes (ESP) has thus evolved into a key area in language education, aligning language learning goals with professional realities. To meet these demands, innovative pedagogical approaches are required-among which Problem-Based Learning (PBL) stands out as an effective and transformative methodology. PBL fosters learner autonomy, critical thinking, and real-world problem-solving skills. Within the context of ESP, where communicative tasks are tightly linked to professional domains, PBL enables students to engage in meaningful interactions that simulate workplace communication. However, implementing PBL in ESP classrooms presents unique challenges: designing authentic problems, managing group dynamics, aligning tasks with language proficiency levels, and assessing complex outcomes are only a few examples. This article investigates how PBL can be effectively integrated into ESP instruction. Drawing on theoretical models, practical examples, and empirical research-especially from Uzbek and international contexts-we explore classroom strategies, pedagogical innovations, and the difficulties encountered during implementation. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to improving the quality of ESP teaching through PBL and preparing students for successful professional communication in their fields.

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has gained traction in language education for its potential to engage learners in solving authentic, real-world problems, thereby developing both language skills and higher-order thinking. In the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), particularly for Economics students, PBL offers opportunities for integrating discipline-specific content with language instruction. However, there are significant challenges in classroom practice that must be addressed to realize its full potential. This article reviews the literature on PBL in Economics/ESP, describes typical classroom practices, identifies obstacles in implementation, and offers recommendations to overcome them. Through a synthesis of case studies, empirical research, and theoretical perspectives, this paper aims to provide practitioners in ESP for Economics with insights and strategies to effectively integrate PBL.

Problem-Based Learning originates in medical education and has since spread to other disciplines. The core features of PBL include student - centeredness, small group work, real/proximal problems, self-directed learning, integration of disciplines, and facilitators guiding rather than lecturing. Key learning outcomes typically targeted are critical thinking, collaboration, problem solving, application of theory to practice, and transferable skills. In language learning, these features translate into tasks where language is both a tool and a goal. Students must use reading, writing, listening, and speaking for authentic purposes-research, discussion, presentation-rather than for isolated drills.

ESP refers to English instruction designed to meet the specific needs of learners in disciplines, professions, or academic contexts. In the Economics domain, ESP would include specialized vocabulary (macroeconomics, microeconomics, econometrics, finance, policy, etc.), conventions of economic discourse, interpreting graphs and data, reading research articles, writing reports or essays, participating in discussions/debates about policies, etc. ESP differs from general English in that its content, methodology, assessment, and sometimes materials are tailored to students' target disciplines. Needs analysis is central: learners' immediate and future uses of English must be identified, which in Economics can include reading academic journals, writing policy briefs, delivering presentations, and using English in business/economic research. There are several reasons why PBL is particularly suitable for Economics ESP:

The domain itself deals with problems-economic issues, policy questions, business challenges-that can serve as authentic problems for students.

Economics students need not only to know theories but also apply them in contexts; PBL supports this transfer.

PBL fosters higher-order thinking: analytical skills, evaluation, synthesis, which are essential in Economics (e.g., interpreting data, evaluating policy).

PBL encourages active learning, increasing motivation and engagement.

However, integrating PBL into ESP for Economics is not straightforward. It requires thoughtful design, materials, teacher training, assessment changes, institutional support, time, and resources.

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has become an influential and widely adopted instructional approach across various academic disciplines due to its learner-centered philosophy, emphasis on real-world relevance, and development of higher-order cognitive skills. In the realm of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and particularly in English for Economics, PBL offers a dynamic and contextually meaningful alternative to traditional language instruction. Rather than relying on teacher-centered lectures or isolated grammar exercises, PBL encourages learners to engage with authentic economic problems that mirror professional challenges in their future careers. This engagement necessitates the use of English in context, thereby facilitating language acquisition in tandem with domain-specific knowledge development. The integration of PBL into ESP for Economics not only enhances linguistic -competence but also promotes critical thinking, collaboration, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. However, implementing PBL in such contexts is not without its challenges. Instructors must navigate a range of pedagogical, logistical, institutional, and learner-related obstacles. These include varying language proficiencies, limited exposure to disciplinary content, insufficient resources, time constraints, and resistance to pedagogical change. Despite these challenges, the potential benefits of PBL in Economics ESP classrooms are substantial and merit in-depth exploration.

Assessment in PBL also differs from conventional models. Rather than relying solely on exams or quizzes, assessment may include rubrics evaluating the final product (e.g., a report or presentation), group process, individual contributions, and the quality of research and reasoning. Both formative and summative assessments are important. Formative assessments help guide learning during the process, while summative assessments evaluate the outcomes. Self-assessment and peer evaluation are also often included to promote metacognitive awareness and accountability. While the pedagogical advantages of PBL are numerous, implementing it in ESP courses, particularly for Economics students, is not without complications. One of the most significant challenges is the variation in students' English language proficiency. In many classrooms, students possess diverse levels of competence, with some struggling to understand academic texts or express complex ideas in English. These difficulties can hinder participation in group discussions, limit the depth of analysis, and reduce confidence. Moreover, students who are not proficient may become overly reliant on stronger group members or disengage entirely. Instructors must address these disparities through scaffolding, differentiated instruction, and supportive group dynamics. Another major challenge lies in the dual expertise required of instructors.

Teaching ESP for Economics using PBL requires knowledge not only of English language pedagogy but also of Economics content. In many institutions, instructors may be trained in language teaching but lack a deep understanding of economic concepts, trends, and discourse conventions. This gap can make it difficult to design realistic and meaningful problem scenarios, provide accurate content feedback, or evaluate the quality of students' solutions. Collaboration between language instructors and Economics faculty can help bridge this gap, but such collaboration is not always feasible due to institutional silos or scheduling

constraints. Resource constraints also affect PBL implementation. Effective PBL often requires access to up-to-date materials, including economic data, academic journals, case studies, statistical software, and digital tools for collaboration and presentation. In contexts where internet access is limited or library holdings are insufficient, students may struggle to conduct the necessary research. Furthermore, PBL requires more time than traditional instruction. The process of understanding the problem, researching it, developing solutions, and preparing deliverables can span several weeks. In rigid curricula with fixed syllabi and high-stakes assessments, allocating sufficient time for PBL may be difficult. The attitudes and expectations of students also play a role. Learners accustomed to teacher-led instruction may feel uncertain or frustrated in PBL environments where the path to learning is less clear. Some students may resist group work due to prior negative experiences or cultural preferences for individual learning. Others may lack the self-regulation skills needed for autonomous learning. It is important for instructors to anticipate these reactions and to provide orientation, guidance, and support throughout the PBL process. Additionally, institutional structures can either support or hinder PBL. Administrative buy-in is essential for scheduling, resource allocation, class size management, and curriculum flexibility. In institutions where performance is measured primarily through standardized tests or where teaching is oriented toward exam preparation, PBL may be viewed as inefficient or risky. Advocating for PBL requires evidence of its effectiveness, as well as a willingness to innovate and experiment. Despite these challenges, numerous studies and classroom reports demonstrate that PBL can be successfully integrated into ESP for Economics with thoughtful planning and adaptation. For example, in several university programs, PBL has been used to engage students in analyzing economic crises, designing business plans, simulating trade negotiations, and evaluating government policy. These projects not only enhance students' understanding of Economics but also improve their English proficiency and increase motivation. Students report that they find the tasks meaningful and relevant, and instructors note improvements in participation, critical thinking, and language use.

To facilitate the successful implementation of PBL in Economics ESP, several strategies can be recommended. First, needs analysis should be conducted at the beginning of the course to determine students' language levels, academic backgrounds, and learning goals. This information can inform the design of problem scenarios and the selection of texts and tasks. Second, scaffolding should be provided throughout the PBL process. This can include vocabulary glossaries, reading guides, writing templates, and examples of past student work. Third, instructors should receive training in both PBL methodology and Economics content, or work collaboratively with Economics faculty. Fourth, group work should be carefully structured to promote equitable participation and effective collaboration. Roles can be assigned within groups to ensure that all members contribute, and peer evaluations can be used to monitor group dynamics. Fifth, assessment should be aligned with PBL goals and include a balance of product- and process-oriented measures. Finally, student orientation is crucial. Learners need to understand the purpose and benefits of PBL, how it works, and what is expected of them. Providing opportunities for reflection and feedback throughout the course can help students adjust and grow.

In conclusion, integrating PBL into ESP for Economics represents a promising and pedagogically sound approach to language and content learning. It aligns with the needs of 21st-century learners by fostering not only linguistic competence but also analytical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and real-world communication skills. While challenges exist in terms of language proficiency, instructor preparation, resources, time, student attitudes, and institutional support, these can be mitigated through careful design, collaboration, and

reflective practice. The transformation from passive learning to active engagement can enrich students' educational experience and better prepare them for the demands of academic and professional life in the field of Economics.

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО И РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается проблема развития способностей при изучении английского языка, глубоко понимать основы, обеспечивающие возможность эффективно использовать свои знания в любой ситуации, то есть формирование функциональной грамотности, позволяющей учащимся эффективно использовать в жизни имеющиеся у них знания, приобретенные в процессе обучения английскому и русскому языку.

Ключевые слова: функциональная грамотность, читательская грамотность, работа с текстом, стратегии чтения.

В настоящее время изучение английского и русского языков все больше и больше становится средством жизнеобеспечения общества. Роль этих языков возрастает в связи с развитием международных научных, экономических, социальных, культурных связей. Изучение английского и русского языков дает возможность распространять особенности русской культуры и осваивать культуру англоязычных стран. Основной задачей обучения английскому и русскому языкам является формирование у обучающихся речевых навыков: чтения, письма, монологической и диалогической речи. Такая деятельность осуществляется на протяжении всего периода обучения.

При обучении английскому и русскому языкам особое внимание уделяется развитию коммуникативных способностей, формированию навыков свободного общения. При этом ни для кого не секрет, что в процессе обучения учителя часто сталкиваются с определенными проблемами и затруднениями обучающихся при работе с текстом. Так, школьники не всегда могут определять значения многих слов, не всегда понимают, как озаглавить текст, затрудняются в подборе ключевых слов, неверно формулируют вопросы по прочитанному тексту.

В чем же причина подобных проблем и затруднений? Прежде всего, это связано с недостаточно развитым уровнем функциональной читательской грамотности школьников. Под функциональной грамотностью понимается «способность человека использовать навыки чтения и письма в условиях его взаимодействия с социумом (оформить счет в банке, прочитать инструкцию, заполнить анкету обратной связи и т.д.), то есть это тот уровень грамотности, который дает человеку возможность вступать в отношения с внешней средой и максимально быстро адаптироваться и функционировать в ней» [3, с. 4].

В связи с этим, в современном преподавании как английского, так и русского языка обучение чтению «не может ограничиваться академическими целями, оно должно включать функциональные и операционные цели, связанные с повседневной жизнью и трудовой деятельностью» [3, с. 10]. Программа обучения языкам на разных ступенях предполагает формирование навыков и умений, без которых сегодня невозможно справиться с решением жизненно важных задач.

Подобные навыки и умения включают в себя умение осмысленно читать и воспринимать на слух, а также продуцировать тексты разных типов (информационного и прикладного характера, литературные тексты); умение извлекать информацию из разных источников; способность находить и критически оценивать информацию из СМИ и Интернета; умение пользоваться источниками и ссылаться на них; умение читать таблицы, диаграммы, схемы, условные обозначения и применять их при подготовке собственных текстов; способность реализовывать различные стратегии чтения при работе с текстом.

Таким образом, мы видим, что современные образовательные стандарты ориентируют учителя на повышение уровня функциональной грамотности учащихся. Так что же характеризует ученика, у которого сформированы навыки читательской грамотности? Прежде всего, это ученик, который может «свободно использовать навыки чтения и письма для получения информации из текста – для его понимания, сжатия, преобразования и т.д.» (А.А. Леонтьев).

Ученик, у которого сформированы навыки функциональной читательской грамотности, умеет использовать различные виды чтения (изучающее, просмотровое, ознакомительное). Такой ученик способен переходить от одной системы приемов чтения и понимания текста к другой, адекватной данной цели чтения и понимания и данному виду текстов [2, с. 6].

Безусловно, для того, чтобы формировать и развивать навыки функциональной грамотности учащихся, учителю необходимо подбирать либо составлять соответствующие задания. При этом, при составлении заданий по функциональной грамотности учителю важно ответить самому на следующие вопросы: какую цель они преследуют, какой уровень понимания текста закрепляют или проверяют?

В исследовании PISA, как отмечают Л.Рождественская, И.Логвина, грамотность чтения подразделяется на следующие уровни: 1) поиск в тексте нужной информации по простому критерию (самый низкий уровень); 2) поиск в тексте нужной информации

по множественным критериям; 3) поиск в тексте нужной информации, распознавание связи между отрывками информации, работа с известной, но противоречивой информацией; 4) поиск и установление последовательности или комбинации отрывков, содержащих глубоко скрытую информацию, умение сделать вывод о том, какая информация в тексте необходима для выполнения задания; 5) понимание сложных текстов и их интерпретация, формулирование выводов и гипотез относительно содержания текста [2, с. 6].

Одним из самых типовых заданий, направленных на поиск в тексте конкретной информации, являются задания на выбор альтернатив – верно/неверно. Учитель обрабатывает важные (или трудные для понимания) места в тексте с помощью инструмента «верно-неверно», и затем предлагает ответить на эти вопросы ученикам. Ученик несколько раз внимательно просматривает текст с определенной целью – найти нужную информацию или убедиться, что она отсутствует в тексте. Но может быть и более дальновидное использование заданий типа «верно-неверно». Например, можно предложить ученикам самим обработать текст, применив этот инструмент.

Формулировки заданий на выбор альтернатив могут быть следующими: 1. Отметь значком * правильный вариант ответа, согласно тексту. 2. Прочитай текст. Выбери правильный вариант ответа (один из предложенных), согласно тексту. 3. Какое из утверждений соответствует тексту? 4. Прочитай текст и отметь «галочкой» то, о чем НЕ сообщается в тексте. При отборе текстов необходимо руководствоваться следующими критериями: актуальность текста для учащихся; учет возрастных особенностей целевой группы (адаптированность текста); наличие новой (для учащихся) информации; наличие фактов, понятий, имен, географических названий, наименований товаров, цифр, дат и т.д.; наличие иллюстраций, схем, диаграмм; наличие в тексте «фактов и мнений» [1, с. 35].

К отличительным особенностям тестов на проверку функционального чтения относят: большой объем текста; неадаптированный текст; информация, представленная в виде рисунков, схем, диаграмм, таблиц, графиков; задания, для выполнения которых требуется интеграция знаний из разных предметов; задания, в которых неясно, к какой области знаний надо обратиться.

Важно соблюдать некоторые правила отбора сплошных текстов к заданиям на функциональное чтение: 1. Текст должен быть ученику интересен. 2. Текст должен содержать неизвестную ученику информацию. 3. Текст должен развивать кругозор. 4. Текст не должен быть перегружен цифрами, датами, терминами. 5. Иллюстрации не отвлекают, а помогают разобраться в содержании текста. Иллюстрации должны способствовать развитию познавательной активности. 6. Уровень трудности текста должен соответствовать возрасту ученика. При необходимости нужно адаптировать текст. 7. Незнакомые слова должны «вычитываться» из текста или быть представлены в сносках. 8. Объем текста не должен превышать норму. 9. Шрифт должен помогать ученику легко читать текст. 10. Текст должен быть структурирован. 11. В тексте не должно быть ошибок [1, с. 46]. Разновидностью данного типа заданий являются задания на поиск информации мелким шрифтом (встречаются даже в некоторых тестах PISA: школьникам предлагается проанализировать содержимое обложки журнала или книги или, например, CD-диска с фильмом, а также сделать выводы о характере произведения, его названии, авторах и т.д.)

Однако, оказывается, что наши ученики иногда затрудняются с правильной интерпретацией иллюстраций, ярких заголовков и рекламных вставок. Все перечисленное тоже относится к тексту, который в терминологии PISA, называется не

сплошным текстом. Это могут быть театральные билеты, программки, постеры, небольшие афиши, входные билеты на культурные мероприятия, проездные билеты, схемы проезда, планы выставок и музеев, скриншоты сайтов и т.д.

Таким образом, мы видим, что основными упражнениями для развития функциональной грамотности являются различные виды работы с текстом. Как уже отмечалось, для того, чтобы текст стал реальной и продуктивной основой обучения всем видам речевой деятельности, важно научить учащихся различным операциям с материалами текста с учетом его жанровых и стилистических особенностей. Этой цели служат различные задания, создаваемые на базе изучаемых текстов.

Как известно, в учебной литературе кроме заданий на собственно чтение и перевод текста, существуют также предтекстовые, текстовые и послетекстовые задания. Подобные задания направлены на лучшее понимание содержания текста, на отработку и усвоение лексико-грамматического материала, на развитие навыков письма и устной речи, а также на развитие различных мыслительных навыков, навыков применения информации, ее анализа, оценивания.

При подготовке для работы на уроке текстового материала преподаватель может самостоятельно разработать подобные задания с учетом хода педагогического процесса в группе, а также с учетом особенностей учащихся. При этом задания могут предъявляться учащимся дифференцированно, в зависимости от их уровня владения языковым материалом. Работа с текстом может осуществляться как на начальном, так и на последующих этапах обучения. Для учащихся более высокого уровня целесообразно разрабатывать и применять задания повышенной сложности, а также проблемные задания, использовать тексты с мыслительной задачей.

Рассмотрим некоторые виды заданий при работе с текстом. Предтекстовые задания направлены на моделирование фоновых знаний, необходимых и достаточных для восприятия конкретного текста, на устранение смысловых и языковых трудностей его понимания и одновременно на формирование навыков и умений чтения, выработку "стратегии понимания", умения прогнозирования. Например: - прочитай заглавие и скажи, о чем (о ком) будет идти речь в данном тексте; - посмотри на фото; скажи, какую жизнь могут вести люди, изображенные на фото; - опиши картинку (соответствующую тематике текста); затем прочти текст и найди ошибки в картинке; - дай определение следующим словам; - соедини слова с их определениями; - определи различные значения одного и того же слова; - найди в тексте предложения с определенной грамматической формой; - прочти первые предложения абзацев и назови вопросы, которые будут рассматриваться в тексте. В текстовых заданиях учащимся предлагаются коммуникативные установки, в которых содержатся указания на вид чтения (изучающее, ознакомительное, просмотровое, поисковое), скорость и необходимость решения определенных познавательных-коммуникативных задач в процессе чтения.

Кроме этого, учащиеся выполняют ряд упражнений с текстом, обеспечивающих формирование соответствующих конкретному виду чтения навыков и умений. Например: - прочти текст; раздели его на смысловые части, подбери названия к каждой из них; - выдели в тексте элементы, которые несут ключевую информацию; - составь план текста; - заполни пропуски в тексте словами в определенной грамматической форме; - передай основную идею текста несколькими предложениями. Послетекстовые задания предназначены для проверки понимания прочитанного, для контроля над степенью сформированности умений чтения и использования полученной информации: - ответь на вопросы по содержанию текста; - выбери правильный ответ

(тест по содержанию текста); - заполни таблицу по содержанию текста; - пронумеруй события в порядке их очередности; - заполни предложения словами из текста; - вырази свое отношение к прочитанному; - составь вопросы к тексту; - подготовь пересказ (аннотацию, рецензию) текста.

Проблемные задания могут входить в систему всех текстовых заданий в качестве завершающего этапа работы над текстом, так как они являются наиболее трудным, творческим видом работы. В системе проблемных заданий можно выделить однокстовые и многоткстовые проблемные задачи.

Примеры однокстовых проблемных заданий: - к тексту, в котором пропущена какая-либо композиционная часть, дать как можно больше вариантов этой части; - скажите, о чем может быть текст, в котором пропущены все тематические слова; дайте как можно больше вариантов, каждый раз вставляя пропущенные слова; - составьте несколько текстов из перемешанных частей текста, каждый раз располагая эти части по-новому; - найдите выход из ситуации (на базе рассказов-головоломок).

Примеры многоткстовых проблемных заданий: - прочтите тексты, выражающие разные точки зрения по одному вопросу; какую еще точку зрения можно высказать? - соедините два текста, выражающих разные точки зрения, в один, как будто его писал один автор. Таким образом, использование на уроках как английского, так и русского языка различного вида текстовых заданий способствует формированию навыков функциональной читательской грамотности обучающихся и комплексному освоению основных видов речевой деятельности, а также развивает творческое мышление, приучает школьников к более серьезной работе с текстом.

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ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ И ПУТИ ЕЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У БУДУЩИХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: Проблема формирования толерантности связанная с тем, что сегодня на первый план выдвигаются ценности и принципы, необходимые для общего выживания и свободного развития (этика и стратегия ненасилия, идея

терпимости к чужим и чуждым позициям, ценностям, культурам, идея диалога и взаимопонимания, поиска взаимоприемлемых компромиссов и т.п.).

Ключевые слова: толерантность, педагогическая толерантность, педагог, родители, дети, нравственность, социальная среда.

Толерантность – особое нравственное качество, отражающее активную социальную позицию и психологическую готовность к позитивному взаимодействию с людьми или группами иной национальной, религиозной, социальной среды, иных взглядов, мировоззрений, стилей мышления и поведения.

Большая роль в этом процессе отводится созданию единого поликультурного пространства, одним из важных составляющих которого является образовательная среда. В настоящий момент проблема создания поликультурной среды решается на уровне всех ступеней образования дошкольного, школьного, вузовского, послевузовского.

Толерантность являет собой новую основу педагогического общения учителя и ученика сущность которого сводится к таким принципам обучения, которые создают оптимальные условия для формирования у обучающихся культуры достоинства, самовыражения личности, исключают фактор боязни неправильного ответа.

Толерантность – это терпимое, уважительное отношение к людям, признание права каждого человека и индивидуальное поведение в рамках законов, принятых обществом. Задача педагога в том, чтобы изучить особенности поведения школьника и оказать ему необходимую педагогическую поддержку. Педагогическая толерантность требует соблюдения некоторых основных принципов:

-все работники образовательного учреждения и родители в общении с детьми должны проявлять к ним доброжелательность, терпение, уважение;

-педагоги должны относиться к ученикам с одинаковым уважением, не возвышая одних за счёт унижения других;

-оценки должны способствовать развитию ребёнка, стимулировать получение знаний и умений, а не быть кнутом в руках педагога;

-процесс обучения невозможен без продуктивного позитивного общения, в ходе которого закладываются нормы и правила поведения, формируется отношение к людям и к жизни [2, с. 210].

На сегодняшний день возникает необходимость воспитания культуры толерантности с самых первых дней обучения. На наш взгляд, воспитание толерантности невозможно в условиях авторитарного стиля общения «учитель - ученик». Поэтому одним из условий является освоение учителем определенных демократических механизмов в организации учебного процесса и общения учеников друг с другом и с учителем.

Именно в начальной школе важно научить ребенка, с одной стороны, принимать другого как значимого и ценного, а с другой стороны критически относиться к своим собственным взглядам. Ориентация педагога на постижение смыслов поведения и поступков детей означает, что в воспитательной деятельности на первый план выходят задачи понимания ребенка. Воспитание культуры толерантности, на наш взгляд, должно осуществляться по формуле: "родители + дети + учитель" [1, с. 56].

В основе педагогической деятельности учителя должен быть живой смысл и живое общение на основе живого слова, живого понятия, что, в свою очередь, важно не само по себе, а как путь не просто к толерантности, пониманию, а путь к толерантному взаимодействию, пониманию взаимному. Здесь можно апеллировать к

симпатическому пониманию, которое исповедовал Г.Г. Шпет, сочувственному (эмпатическому) М.М. Бахтин, к пониманию через сомышление [5, с. 78].

Можно выделить две группы методов понимания:

1. Методы интерпретации. При интерпретации педагогом поведения ребенка исходной позицией является признание ребенка, уважение его «самости», индивидуальности, понимание того, что его поведение имеет для него самого субъективный, аутентичный смысл.

2. Методы, помогающие педагогу постичь внутренний мир ребенка в его своеобразии и целостности, проникнуть в глубину его переживаний, опираясь на чувства исследователя и интуицию. Данный подход связан с процессом развертывания человеческого отношения одного человека к другому, что предполагает толерантное, соучастное отношение, эмпатийное, а значит, на основе диалога.

Толерантность профессионально необходимое личное качество педагога, диктуемое задачами, содержанием и характером его деятельности. Проблема осложняется тем, что это качество связано взаимоотношениями не только с детьми (они уже сами по себе весьма непросты!), но и со взрослыми. Чтобы предупредить, избежать, преодолеть столкновение авторитетов, важно щадить родительское самолюбие при публичных индивидуальных характеристиках детей; сдерживать эмоции, общаясь с «трудными» для себя родителями; больше интересоваться домашними условиями ребят и полнее информировать о различных сторонах жизни детского коллектива (а не только «об успеваемости и посещаемости»); фиксировать внимание пусть на небольших, но успехах ребенка.

Самая деликатная проблема – толерантность в отношениях между педагогами, прежде и острее всего между учителями. Это проблема, которая касается специалистов, работающих в общих пространстве и атмосфере, формально в едином статусе. Однако, будучи специалистами-педагогами, они являются при этом разными людьми, а известная замкнутость этого мира, постоянное нервное напряжение в нем, дефицит мужской сдержанности, стремительная, часто непредсказуемо развивающаяся череда ситуаций обостряют значимость толерантности.

В этих условиях чрезвычайно важны умение всех и каждого быть снисходительным, мириться с существованием иного мнения, осознанно стремиться к достижению согласия в решении педагогических вопросов, единства требований.

Особая роль принадлежит усилиям учителя по самовоспитанию толерантности. Оно связано в первую очередь с осознанием своего профессионального достоинства, предполагающего, наряду ссамоуважением, способность уважать других -иных людей, в том числе и детей. Не менее важны рефлексия, самоанализ своего реализуемого отношения к разным окружающим, честная, не вызванная эмоциональным возбуждением оценка своих мыслей, отношений, решений, поступков. Смысл деятельности педагога -создание условий не только для формирования и проявления толерантности одного (одних), но и преодоления вызывающего негативизм в поведении или общении другого (других). Это явления разные, но единые по воспитывающейнаправленности: любой негативизм и субъекта, и объекта толерантности имеет свои причины, и важно преодолеть как внешне проявляющиеся следствия, так и их причины.

Средства решения этих задач могут быть различны. Прежде всего, целесообразно, повторим, организовать жизнедеятельность ребят так, чтобы одни могли проявить, а другие увидеть хорошее в ком-то или чем-то. Идти таким путем

значит стимулировать, «провоцировать» общие дела, позволяющие лучше узнать друг друга, взаимодействуя, помогая, радуясь удаче, преодолевая трудности. Гораздо сложнее помочь ребятам понять внешкольную среду, противоречивость социального фона их жизни, от непосредственного окружения (семья, приятельские компании) до явлений общественной жизни (социальное расслоение, материальные трудности, общественное настроение). Особенно актуальным становится знание, постоянное изучение современного детства: его идиологов, привязанностей, представлений, и динамики развития каждого школьника.

Ведь улавливая новое, легче увидеть причины возникающих трудностей и конфликтов, а, следовательно, легче искать способы развития толерантности. [6, с. 75]

Понятие «культура мира» не сводится к общеупотребительным дефинициям «культура» как художественно-творческая область и «мир» как Вселенная. Речь идёт о создании цивилизации, ориентированной на мир и ненасилие. «Культура мира» это сочетание ценностных установок, мировоззренческих взглядов, традиций, типов поведения и образцов жизни» построения культуры мира ключевая роль отводится образованию как незаменимому пути к культуре мира. [6, с. 88]

Концепция культуры мира выдвинула задачу кардинального обновления:

- а) содержания образования;
- б) методов и технологий обучения;
- в) сложившихся принципов взаимоотношений «учитель–ученик»;
- г) всей атмосферы школьной жизни.

Отмечается, что изменения в духе культуры мира и толерантности должны коснуться всех звеньев образовательной системы от детского сада до институтов повышения квалификации учителей. Рекомендуется использовать три основных пути:

- а) в процессе изучения всех предметов;
- б) через междисциплинарные связи;
- в) в виде специальных курсов и занятий.

Теперь следует привести рабочее определение категории «толерантность», специализированное по отношению к системе высшего профессионального образования: толерантность есть особая форма выражения субъектами вузовского образовательного процесса своего отношения к окружающему миру в единстве всех его проявлений, предполагающая ту или иную форму согласия, основанного на всестороннем многоплановом анализе сущностных связей и отношений зависимости между объектами, процессами и явлениями. При этом данный анализ позволяет сформировать взвешенную точку зрения, учитывающую полярные и внешне несовместимые компоненты, провести их к состоянию, выражаемому терминами «единство», «существование», «взаимодополнительность». Для преподавателя при этом целесообразно выделить четыре компонента:

- а) толерантность как качество личности, проявляемое за рамками профессиональной деятельности;
- б) толерантность ученого -исследователя;
- в) толерантность в контексте учебно-методической деятельности;
- г) «профессиональная толерантность», проявляемая в ежедневной педагогической деятельности, включающей процесс педагогического взаимодействия со студентами и систему «профессиональных отношений» с коллегами и администрацией вуза.

Для студента высшего учебного заведения целесообразно разделить проблему на три составляющие по аналогии с представленным выше выделением:

а) «толерантность общения», не связанная непосредственно с учебным процессом;

б) «толерантность формирующегося специалиста» в единстве и многообразии всех его профессиональных качеств;

в) толерантность, проявляемая в процессе педагогического взаимодействия с преподавателями. [3, 56 с.]

Особо следует отметить возможность формирования культуры толерантности при опоре непосредственно на содержание изучаемых на различных ступенях вузовского обучения учебных дисциплин. К конкретным возможностям содержания вузовского образования в плане формирования толерантности относятся:

-иллюстрация противоположных, взаимоисключающих сторон, свойств, отношений в изучаемых объектах, процессах и явлениях

-фактически иллюстрация диалектического закона единства и борьбы противоположностей; иллюстрация такого типа мышления, который ориентируется не столько на расчленение "противоборствующих" свойств и отношений, сколько на их единство, обеспечивающее целостность существования изучаемого объекта или процесса, их внутреннюю гармонию; акцент внимания на возможности описания изучаемого объекта или процесса, единых и целостных в своей сути различными методами, способами и средствами (порой даже полярными), каждый из которых в отдельности не дает полного и законченного описания и продуктивно лишь их совместное использование;

-использование историко-научных и биографических фактов и сведений, иллюстрирующих, как проявлялось отмеченное качество в конкретных фрагментах истории научного познания. [2, с. 132]

Также важно отметить возможности формирования толерантности в процессе педагогического общения "преподаватель-студент" -и прежде всего путем представления преподавателем некоего условного образца, эталона толерантности в самых различных ситуациях как в процессе аудиторного, так и внеаудиторного неформального общения: в процессе руководства преподавателем дипломными, курсовыми, реферативными работами студентов, в ходе производственной практики, а также диспутов, творческих встреч и научных конференций. Это обстоятельство необходимо учитывать при проектировании и реализации магистерских программ по педагогическому образованию при организации подготовки преподавателей высшей школы; педагогов дополнительного образования и других работников образования. [7, с. 90]

Очень важен в контексте категории "толерантность" и принцип сотрудничества педагогов, обучаемых и руководителей образовательных учреждений профессионального образования, основанного на доверительности, взаимопонимании и взаимной требовательности, предполагающей широкие деловые контакты, совместную постановку задач и анализ результатов, позволяющий реализовать и принцип саморазвития личности педагога, учащегося, администратора.

Таким образом, очевидно, что рассматриваемая категория "толерантность", с одной стороны, интегративная, многоаспектная и многоплановая проблема, проектирующаяся как на содержание профессионального образования, так и на методы организации учебно-познавательной деятельности студентов, как на формирование

у них системы знаний, так и широкого комплекса мыслительных умений, а с другой сложное, многокомпонентное качество личности, сформированность которого обуславливает ту или иную степень успешности социального и профессионального функционирования

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СПОСОБЫ ВОСПИТАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ РУССКОЙ РЕЧИ У СТУДЕНТОВ-НЕФИЛОЛОГОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ГУМАНИТАРНЫХ ДИСЦИПЛИН

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются потенциальные возможности воспитания культуры русской речи при изучении гуманитарных дисциплин студентами-нефилологами. Раскрывается воспитательный потенциал курса «Русский язык и культура речи». В заключении подчеркивается, что работа по формированию речевой культуры студентов сложна, важна, длительна и многогранна и только совместными усилиями всех педагогов можно воспитать грамотных востребованных специалистов.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, культура речи, студент-нефилолог, компетенция, профессионализм.

В профессиональной подготовке будущих специалистов, наряду с формированием и развитием профессиональных компетенций, существенную роль играет воспитание в них коммуникативной культуры, обеспечивающей им комфортное существование и успех в общении не только с коллегами, но и со всеми людьми, с

которыми приходится им иметь дело при выполнении своих функциональных обязанностей.

Сегодня практически все организации оценивают и отбирают себе такие кадры, которые проявляют компетентность и находчивость в своей области деяний. Причем речевой имидж – важнейшая составляющая их профессионализма. Именно поэтому владение русским языком и культурой речи является необходимой частью их творческого состояния. Для того чтобы быть востребованным, занять достойное место в коллективе, добиться несомненных успехов в работе требуется от современного человека развитие коммуникативных качеств, а именно:

- знание канонов современной риторики;
- овладение умением решать коммуникативные и речевые задачи в конкретной ситуации общения;
- накопление опыта анализа и создания профессионально значимых типов высказываний;
- развитие творчески активной речевой личности, умеющей применять полученные знания и сформированные умения в разнообразных актах общения и т.д. [5, 134-с.].

Нельзя не согласиться с мнением Л.А. Введенской «Ошибки в речи малограмотного человека свидетельствуют о его низкой общей культуре, ошибки в речи образованного человека свидетельствуют о его небрежном отношении к своей речи, о безответственном отношении к своей работе, своим обязанностям». [3, с. 76]

Давайте задумаемся над вопросом чему же необходимо в первую очередь обучить студента-нефилолога, будущего специалиста? Ответ на этот вопрос очевиден – помочь ему осознать, что его будущая профессиональная деятельность – это своеобразный бесконечный диалог: прежде всего диалог с самим собой, коллегами, партнерами, руководством. Наш выпускник должен помнить о речевой ответственности, ведь он является носителем гражданского самосознания и хранителем речевой культуры, русского литературного языка. Практика показывает, что большинство студентов владеет, в лучшем случае, диалогической речью, которая имеет свои особенности, проявляющиеся в использовании специфических языковых средств, допустимых в разговорной речи (жестов, интонации, мимики), но неприемлемых в построении монолога, который строится по законам книжного литературного языка.

Владение связной монологической речью – высшее достижение речевой культуры носителя русского языка. Оно вбирает в себя освоение звуковой культуры языка, словарного состава, грамматического строя и происходит в тесной связи с развитием всех сторон речи – фонетической, лексической, грамматической.

Однако, как показывают наблюдения, обучающиеся не могут правильно составлять связные высказывания, испытывают всегда психологический дискомфорт в процессе самого публичного выступления. Из-за этого развитие связной речи их тормозится: она становится менее раскованной и эмоциональной, механизм более трафаретной. Вообще, следует отметить, что формирование способности монологического устного речевого воздействия на партнера – не решенная еще проблема для всего современного общества. Это обстоятельство детерминирует необходимость усиления внимания преподавателей-русистов к вопросам разработки эффективных подходов к развитию у будущих специалистов умений и навыков правильной искусственной речи.

Воспитание речевой культуры студентов-нефилологов осуществляется обычно на занятиях по всем дисциплинам гуманитарной направленности. Но, на наш взгляд, особое внимание следует уделять курсу «Русский язык и культура речи». Воспитательной целью дисциплины, изучаемой на первых курсах, выступает использование педагогического потенциала дисциплины для воспитания и развития личностных качеств обучаемых, которые необходимы им для успешной социализации и подготовки к будущей профессиональной деятельности в процессе освоения и принятия системы ценностей, этических норм и правил, регулирующих отношения личности в семье, обществе и государстве. [2, с. 66]

Данная дисциплина готовит к более глубокому восприятию и усвоению всех изучаемых в вузе предметов гуманитарного цикла и профессиональной подготовки и нацелена на формирование у студентов навыков работы с устным и письменным текстом. Мы имеем в виду, прежде всего, те навыки, которые необходимы востребованному обществом специалисту для успешной работы в коллективе, а также для общения в различных сферах коммуникации: бытовой, правовой, научной, социально-государственной. Следовательно, уже на студенческой скамье нужно научить бакалавра устанавливать контакты с людьми, что предполагает готовность его к любому диалогу в соответствии с дискурсом и складывающимся в актах общения ситуациями.

Основная задача курса «Русский язык и культура речи» заключается в формировании у студентов потребности анализировать не только свою, но и чужую речь. А это позволяет им мотивированно использовать языковые средства, которые будут оптимальны при решении коммуникативных задач, связанных с будущей профессиональной деятельностью. [4, с. 98]

Нельзя не упомянуть и то, что теперь наметилась тенденция к сокращению аудиторной нагрузки студентов. Поэтому первостепенное значение имеет сейчас решение дидактических задач, связанных с усилением мотивации студентов к обучению русскому языку и интенсификацией процесса усвоения ими норм хорошей речи благодаря активизации самостоятельной работы во внеаудиторное время. Поскольку культура речи предполагает правильное и уместное употребление языковых средств в определении речевой ситуации и обеспечение наибольшего эффекта в достижении поставленных коммуникативных целей, то в воспитании такой культуры выделяют две стороны педагогического процесса:

- 1) выработку у обучающихся умения говорить и писать правильно – в соответствии с нормами литературного языка;
- 2) формирование у них умения говорить и писать хорошо, искусно – с соблюдением практической стилистики и риторического канона. [6, с. 132]

Для соблюдения современных требований общества к выпускникам технических вузов нами разработана авторская программа курса «Русский язык и культура речи», в которой уделяется самое пристальное внимание таким разделам, как «Нормы современного русского литературного языка», «Основы публичного мастерства», «Функциональные стили речи».

При изучении тех или иных языковых единиц и их конструкций, мы показываем текстообразующий потенциал, раскрываем особенности их функционирования в речи, обучаем студентов нормам литературного языка, обогащением словарного запаса их, грамматический строй их речи синонимами. При этом опираемся на такие понятия как стиль, тип речи и категориальные признаки текста.

Работа по овладению нормами русского литературного языка формирует навыки правильного воспроизведения слова, структуры словосочетания и предложения. Работа по обогащению речи воспитывает умение не только правильно, но и уместно, с учетом требований контекста употреблять языковые средства в речи. При выполнении упражнений, роль которых заключается в выработке указанных умений, включает задания на творческое наблюдение, при этом сопоставляются как нормативный, так и ненормативный варианты, сравниваются слова и обороты близкие по значению.

Тексты, предлагаемые студентам на занятиях, относятся к различным стилям речи, способствуют гуманизации обучения, воспитанию интереса и любви к избранной профессии. В них затрагиваются проблемы науки, экологии, образования. Тематика и содержание связанных текстов соотносится с речевыми темами «Русский язык среди других языков мира», «Воспитание характера», «Культура. Искусство», «Компьютеры: их настоящее и будущее» и др. В результате у студентов расширяется словарный запас, обогащается запас грамматических конструкций, вырабатывается гибкость в обращении с языковыми средствами. Работа эта способствует развитию чувства языка и приучает обучающихся к самооценке речи с позиций правильно/неправильно, лучше/хуже.

Как показывает опытно-экспериментальная работа, эффективность наблюдений за языковыми средствами значительно повышается, если они проводятся как один из этапов профессиональной деятельности. Только в этом случае проблема выбора языкового средства наполняется практически смыслом, становится проблемной ситуацией, а сам выбор получает мотивацию в содержании речи, а также в условиях общения. У студента появляется возможность сказать, прежде всего, самому себе примерно следующее: «Я выбираю именно это языковое средство, потому что оно лучше других передает содержание моей речи в данной речевой ситуации. Если условия общения изменятся, то для передачи этого же содержания я выберу другую конструкцию». Языковая тренировка в таком случае приобретает практически значимый смысл. Такой речевой опыт не проходит бесследно, он закрепляется в памяти.

Следующее направление работы – развитие связной речи студентов-нефилологов. Основное внимание здесь обращается на содержательную сторону высказывания, развитие коммуникативных умений. Это умение определять объем содержания и границы темы, подчинять изложение основной мысли, а также выражать мысли точно, правильно и по возможности ярко. Важно также и умение совершенствовать написанное. Иными словами, система занятий по курсу закрепляет полученные в школе умения ориентироваться в ситуации общения: анализировать мотивы речевой деятельности, условия и задачи общения. Чтобы эта система работала эффективно, необходимо приблизить условия обучения к естественным условиям общения, то есть надо ввести студента в речевую ситуацию и научить его ориентироваться в ней для того, чтобы он ясно представлял себе собеседника, а также условия речи и поставленные задачи общения.

Эта проблема может быть решена с помощью данных функциональной стилистики, факторов, обуславливающих стиль речи: сферы общения – официальная или неофициальная, условий общения – персональная или массовая коммуникация, функции общения – общения, сообщения, воздействия. Стилистика помогает ввести студентов в мыслимую или представляемую речевую ситуацию и вызвать у них потребность в общении. Как показывает практика, наиболее благоприятные условия для совершенствования речи создаются в том случае, если обучение проводится на уровне учебной речевой деятельности, т.е. в условиях, приближенных к естественной

коммуникации, обеспечивающих сознательность в построении высказывания и более высокую мотивацию в обучении.

Большую роль в обучении играет метод моделирования речевого высказывания. Он реализуется в различных видах ситуативных упражнений, основанных на зависимости создаваемых дискурсов от речевой ситуации. Таким образом, ситуативные упражнения повышают речевую культуру и культуру поведения в целом. В этом их большое воспитательное значение.

Что касается раздела «Основы публичного мастерства», то ее роль в развитии коммуникативной культуры студента-нефилолога весьма существенна, поскольку она вооружает их знаниями об ораторском искусстве, зародившемся в Древней Греции получившем развитие в Древнем Риме. Возникновение риторики, рекомендующей правила искусной, целесообразной и убедительной речи, вызвано появившимися более чем две тысячи пятьсот лет назад демократическими формами общественной жизни. Если гражданин не владел публичной речью, это считалось более позорным и постыдным, чем недостатки физического развития.[3, с. 102]

Риторика охватывает все сферы человеческого общения – этическую, эмоциональную и мыслительную или логическую и поэтому является мощнейшим инструментом формирования не только предпринимательских целей, но и взглядов, убеждений людей, коллективов и всего общества в целом. Навыки публичного монолога в жанре убеждающей совещательной речи или речи-размышления в споре студентам необходимо получить, по нашему мнению, именно на практических языковых занятиях в вузе.

В первую очередь выступающему, чтобы достичь определенной универсальности, важно знать правила композиции выступления. Это не так сложно, как кажется на первый взгляд: наука риторика, которой уже больше двух тысяч лет, дает ответ на многие вопросы. Отметим только, что изучение раздела «Основы публичного мастерства» дает возможность решить следующие практические вопросы:

- повысить общую и деловую культуру общения;
- установить деловые связи с людьми, организациями, структурами;
- подготовить и успешно провести деловые переговоры;
- организовать эффективную рекламную компанию фирмы;
- создать творческую атмосферу в коллективе;
- установить благоприятный психологический климат на предприятии;
- усовершенствовать управление фирмой с помощью речевых средств.

Необходимо помнить и о том, что овладение орфоэпической, грамматической, лексической, стилистической нормами – шаг необходимый, но недостаточный для формирования общекультурной компетенции. Актуальна работа над остальными качествами хорошей речи – точностью, логичностью, чистотой, уместностью, богатством и выразительностью. [5, с 90.]

Поэтому при изучении раздела «Основы публичного мастерства» дается краткая история ораторского искусства; рассматриваются такие темы раздела как, этапы построения публичного выступления, поведение оратора, искусство спора, все это необходимо знать для того чтобы повысить уровень владения публичной речью, необходимой для современного специалиста.

В своих научных трудах профессор Г.А. Анисимов отмечает, что «Умению изобретать мысль и проводить ее в жизнь студенты учатся благодаря анализу классических произведений ораторского искусства, в том числе и судебного

красноречия, усвоению риторических правил и занятиям собственной практикой составления речений по этим правилам» [1, 76-с].

Особо рассматриваются такие вопросы, как искусство речи делового человека, искусство речи руководителя предприятия, культура диспутов; обучение риторике в век сети компьютеров и т.д.

Важно отметить, что преподаватели кафедры ОДО КНИТУ уделяют большое внимание формированию творческой языковой личности бакалавров, ибо речь человека – существенная часть внутреннего «Я», это первый показатель развития и интеллектуальной самостоятельности человека. «От культуры слова – к культуре эмоциональной, от эмоциональной культуры – к культуре моральных чувств и поступков» – таков путь к гармонии знаний и нравственности. [5, с. 65].

Наша основная цель – воспитание сильной языковой личности в условиях ориентации на общечеловеческие ценности, возрождение традиций русской духовной культуры, принципы общечеловеческой морали, конечная же цель – обеспечить достойное профессиональное общение, умение вести дискуссию, диалоги с партнерами, вести с ними, если нужно и дискуссии.

Итак, высшая школа сегодня должна готовить профессиональную интеллигенцию, основными чертами которой является высокая духовность и творческая личность. Другими словами, риторика в таком ее понимании становится средством познания действительности, орудием ее совершенствования путем гармонизации отношений с коллегами в процессе общения, а также средством развития творческой личности. [5, с. 98]

Таким образом, успешное воспитание культуры общения обусловлено рядом факторов объективного и субъективного характеров, в совершенствовании речевых умений студентов-нефилологов должны быть заинтересованы все без исключения преподаватели, ибо коммуникативная культура языковой личности является базовой в общем культурном развитии специалиста, в реализации его интеллектуальных и творческих способностей. Работа по формированию речевой культуры студентов сложна, важна, длительна и многогранна. Она должна проводиться не только на занятиях по дисциплине «Русский язык и культура речи», но и на занятиях по всем другим дисциплинам. Только совместными усилиями всех педагогов можно воспитать грамотных востребованных специалистов.

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РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКИ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена особенностям и роли педагогической практики в условиях современного образовательного процесса. В данной статье изложены основные функции педагогической практики, принципы, необходимые для успешного функционирования педагогической системы, выделены компоненты профессиональной компетентности педагога, а также особое внимание уделяется исследовательским возможностям практики.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая практика, педагогическое образование, профессиональная компетентность, модернизация, учебно - воспитательная работа, уровень готовности к самостоятельной жизни, самообучение и самосознание, профессиональная деятельность.

Актуальной проблемой сегодняшнего дня является задача повышения качества подготовки будущих педагогов высшего профессионального образования, решение которой возможно посредством использования эффективных средств, осуществляемых в процессе педагогической практики. В ходе самостоятельной профессиональной деятельности каждый выпускник вуза выполняет педагогические задачи.

Педагогическая практика – неотъемлемая часть образовательного процесса, объединяющая в единое целое теоретические знания, приобретенные умения и навыки, которые применяются в период прохождения практики, цель которой – познание и определение степени готовности человека к самостоятельной работе в школе, приобретение педагогического опыта. [2, с. 86-89].

Вопрос о роли повышения педагогической практики студентов в их деятельности освещали видные ученые И.Ф.Харламов, О.А.Абдуллин, Ш.А.Амонашвили, И.Х.Каримова, Б.К.Кодиров, М.Л.Лутфуллоев, Т.А.Шукуров, И.О.Обидов, Б.Р.Рахимов, Х.Р.Рахимов, Ф.Шарифзода, Ш.А.Шаропов и другие.

В период педагогической практики студент не только готовится к самостоятельной работе, но и создаются условия для развития творческого потенциала его личности как будущего учителя. Педагогическая практика, как основной этап системы высшего образования, носит образовательный и воспитательный характер, обогащает теоретическую подготовку студента, создает условия для использования этих знаний при решении практических задач. В этот период происходит формирование профессиональных навыков и умений.

Важной задачей педагогической практики является воспитание у студентов стойкой любви к профессии учителя, потребности в профессиональном самообразовании, подготовка их к творческому и исследовательскому подходу к педагогической деятельности. Педагогическая практика создаёт условия для саморегуляции и самостоятельности студента как компетентного педагога, способного

работать в условиях конкуренции и в различных типах образовательных учреждений. Реализация этой цели позволяет актуализировать содержание и технологии образования, подготовить педагога, способного: для решения различных социальных и педагогических проблем.

Естественно, при этом необходимо обратиться к исследовательским возможностям практикантов, которые заключаются в следующем:

- выполнение научно-исследовательских работ творческого характера по образовательным дисциплинам в период педагогической практики;
- проведение апробации отдельных методов исследования в период педагогической практики (наблюдение, анкетирование, интервьюирование, анализ документов);
- организация научно-исследовательской работы со студентами в период прохождения педагогической практики;
 - участие студентов в инновационной деятельности коллектива, учебного заведения в рамках педагогической практики (поиск путей и возможностей обоснования инноваций, моделирование, прогнозирование);
 - выполнение курсовых, выпускных и профильных проектов в период прохождения практики. [3, с. 150]

Успешное функционирование педагогической системы может быть основано на последовательной реализации следующих принципов:

- связь теоретического образования с практикой: с одной стороны, усвоение и практическое применение студентами теоретических знаний о человеке и обществе, полученных в ходе изучения общеобразовательных, психолого-педагогических и технических дисциплин, осознание их значимости для успешной профессиональной деятельности, и с другой стороны, закрепление теоретических знаний в ходе изучения теоретических дисциплин научно-исследовательской работы, полученных в ходе практики;
- систематичность и последовательность: поэтапное освоение всех видов профессиональной деятельности, систематическое освоение всех профессиональных задач специалиста;
- преемственность: содержательная связь всех видов опыта.
- постепенное расширение спектра ролей и социальных видов деятельности, в которые вовлечён студент, увеличение объёма и сложности содержания деятельности, которая от курса к курсу становится ближе к профессиональной деятельности. [5, с. 51-55]

Эффективность образовательной и воспитательной деятельности определяется тем, в какой степени отношения в сфере общения и сфере деятельности организованы соответствующим образом, и она тем выше, чем больше процесс образования и воспитания обогащает и перестраивает потребности и желания личности, развивает и усиливает интеллектуальную, эмоциональную и волевою активность учащегося.

В этот период происходит постоянное развитие личностного самосознания, проявляется интерес к познанию и построению карьеры, потребность в труде, умение строить планы самостоятельной жизни, социальной активности, самостоятельности, решаются вопросы выбора карьеры и жизненного пути. Важнейшими задачами студента в период педагогической практики являются наблюдение и изучение жизни детей, деятельности учителей, классных руководителей и их взаимодействия в педагогическом процессе.

Цель педагогической практики - создание условий для самопознания, самосознания и определения личности студента как субъекта профессиональной педагогической деятельности. Педагогическая практика в педагогических вузах в условиях модернизации образования направлена на постепенное формирование личности будущего учителя как профессионального, компетентного педагога, конкурентоспособного на рынке труда.

К основным элементам, способствующим развитию профессиональной компетентности педагога, относятся: умения моделировать педагогический процесс; осуществлять воспитательные воздействия на характер обучающегося; необходимо выстраивать взаимоотношения с каждым обучающимся, содействовать его духовному и познавательному развитию; руководство определением самоопределения, организация самосознания развития личности, создание условий для личностного развития обучающегося как субъекта деятельности.

Содержание компетентности учителя понимается как процесс (педагогическая деятельность, педагогическое общение, идентичность ученика и идентичность учителя) и результат (способность к самостоятельному развитию, самообучению, самосознание учителя). Основным способом определения профессионального уровня будущего учителя является специально организованная деятельность в период подготовки учителя, которая в свете современных требований должна носить исследовательский характер. [1, с. 148-150]

Для будущих педагогов важны компетенции, позволяющие изучать среду обитания, обучения и воспитания детей, динамику развития ребенка, чтобы создать соответствующие условия образовательного учреждения как среды формирования личности.

Для повышения эффективности педагогической практики, на наш взгляд, необходимо:

- четко определить цели и задачи студенческих практик, конкретно указать их содержание, применить теоретические знания на практике, учесть компетенции, которые должны быть сформированы в результате прохождения практики, а также указать критерии оценки результатов деятельности студентов во время прохождения практики;

- определить, что каждый студент должен проходить производственную практику с учетом его интересов, способностей, перспектив его дальнейшего развития и роста;

- оказывать педагогическую помощь студенту в самостоятельном решении возникающих проблем (от выявления проблем до анализа и оценки эффективности выбранных решений).

Подводя итог вышеизложенному, отметим, что учет всех требований к организации педагогической практики не только готовит студентов к профессиональной деятельности, но и развивает у них личностные качества, необходимые будущим учителям.

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НРАВСТВЕННОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ШКОЛЕ И ЕГО ОСОБЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются задачи нравственного воспитания формирование представлений, нравственных чувств, нравственных привычек и норм. Раскрываются практики поведения воспитания гуманных чувств и отношений, коллективизма, дружеских взаимоотношений, культуры поведения, дисциплинированности, трудолюбия, патриотизма, толерантного отношения к людям разных национальностей.

Ключевые слова: развитие, личность, формирование, общество, взаимодействие, среда, убеждения, моральные принципы.

Духовно-нравственное развитие личности-процесс социализации последовательное расширение и укрепление ценностно-смысловой сферы личности, формирование способности человека оценивать и сознательно выстраивать отношения к себе, другим людям, обществу, государству, Отечеству, миру в целом на основе традиционных моральных норм, нравственных идеалов [4, с. 43].

Нравственное воспитание – взаимодействие воспитанника с воспитателем и образовательной средой, которое охватывает все стороны взаимоотношений человека с миром по законам морали и нравственности. В качестве основной цели нравственного воспитания рассматривается развитие нравственной культуры личности. Нравственная культура личности- знание общих моральных принципов, переплавить их в глубоко прочувствованные убеждения, умение применять нормы поведения, находить адекватную им форму поступка.

Формирование нравственной культуры личности зависит от нравственной культуры общества. Личность аккумулирует нравственную культуру общества под действием различных факторов(индивидуальный жизненный опыт, воспитание, искусство, этическое просвещение и др.). Нравственная культура личности-индивидуальное приобретение выраженное в его нравственных идеалах и моральных предпочтениях. Нравственная культура личности проявляется в отношении к природе, другим людям, к труду, учению, искусству. Она находит выражение в умении организовать свою жизнь по законам высокой морали.

Человечность, гуманность, добропорядочность, совесть, добросовестность, ответственность, честность – эти и другие качества, проявляясь в жизни человека, превращают нравственность из теоретической конструкции в реально существующий феномен. Раскрываясь всем богатством своих моральных чувств, убеждений, мотивов и качеств, человек становится неповторимой личностью, открывает и совершенствует, говоря словами Канта, «человеческое в себе», «заложенные в нас прекрасные задатки добра, делающие человека достойным уважения»[3, с. 156].

Нравственная красота раскрывает самое лучшее в человеческой природе и облагораживает его отношения с другими людьми. «Правда о добропорядочном заключается в том еще, что он многое делает ради друзей и отечества и даже умирает за них, если надо: он расточит имущество и почести и вообще блага, за которые держатся другие, оставляя за собою лишь нравственную красоту».

О человеке как источнике истинно человеческого говорил в свое время и Аристотель, раскрывая образ «нравственно прекрасного человека» («добропорядочного»). Добропорядочного человека отличает больше всего то, – писал он, – «что во всех частных случаях он видит истину так, будто он для них мерило и закон». Нравственная красота раскрывает самое лучшее в человеческой природе и облагораживает его отношения с другими людьми. «Правда о добропорядочном заключается в том еще, что он многое делает ради друзей и отечества и даже умирает за них, если надо: он расточит имущество и почести и вообще блага, за которые держатся другие, оставляя за собою лишь нравственную красоту».

Процесс нравственного воспитания учащихся в образовательном учреждении предполагает овладение личностью необходимой суммой этических знаний, их осмысление через эмоционально-образное представление и практическое опробование норм морального поведения, что способствует развитию культуры нравственно-ориентированного мышления и поведения воспитанников.

Воспитание духовности и нравственности как сложных личностных качеств и как активной гражданской позиции школьников одновременно – это воспитательный процесс, который предполагает работу учителя начальных классов по развитию всех компонентов, составляющих структурно-содержательное единство этого процесса, как в предметно-урочной, так и во внеурочной деятельности обучающихся.

Таким образом, можно сказать, что духовно-нравственное развитие и воспитание личности в целом является сложным, многоплановым процессом. Оно неотделимо от жизни человека во всей ее полноте и противоречивости, от семьи, общества, культуры, человечества в целом, от страны проживания и культурно-исторической эпохи, формирующей образ жизни народа и сознание человека.

В условиях изменений, происходящих в современном обществе, у подрастающего поколения возникает необходимость самостоятельного выбора своих ценностных ориентиров.

Учащиеся начальной школы наиболее восприимчивы к духовно-нравственному воспитанию и развитию. С 7 лет ребенок переживает кризис, связанный с осознанием своего «Я» в социуме. Недостатки духовного и нравственного воспитания и развития трудно восполнить в последующие годы. В младшем школьном возрасте (7-11 лет) появляется способность произвольно концентрировать внимание на неинтересных событиях и вещах. Но доминирует произвольное внимание. В этот период внимание характеризуется небольшим объемом и малой устойчивостью (до 10-20 минут).

В 7-11 лет ребенок физически развивается относительно спокойно и равномерно. Увеличение роста и веса, выносливости, жизненной емкости лёгких идет довольно равномерно и пропорционально. Происходит функциональное совершенствование мозга – развивается аналитико-синтетическая функция коры, постепенно изменяется взаимоотношение процессов возбуждения и торможения: процесс торможения становится более сильным, но по-прежнему преобладает процесс возбуждения и младшие школьники в высокой степени возбудимы.

Развитие мотивационно-нравственной сферы означает усвоение системы ценностей и формирование иерархии мотивов личности. Традиционно принято

выделять три главных уровня развития морального сознания индивида: доморальный уровень, когда ребёнок руководствуется своими эгоистическими побуждениями; уровень конвенциональной морали, для которой характерна ориентация на заданные извне нормы и требования; уровень автономной морали, для которой характерна ориентация на устойчивую внутреннюю систему принципов. Для полного описания уровней развития нравственности чаще всего используется теория Л.Колберга. Колберг связывал моральное развитие с интеллектуальным развитием индивида, поскольку от этого зависит степень осознания моральных суждений. Он выделял шесть стадий в развитии моральных суждений.

На первой стадии ребенок оценивает поступки в зависимости от реакции на них взрослых.

Вторая стадия - ребенок на этой стадии стремится максимизировать удовлетворение собственных желаний и потребностей, при этом свести к минимуму негативные последствия.

На третьей стадии ребенок начинает осознавать роль взаимности и доверия, которые лежат в основе взрослых отношений между людьми.

Четвертая стадия-осознание общепринятых стандартов и требований.

На пятой стадии суждение о поступке основывается на уважении прав человека.

На шестой стадии человек оценивает поступки исходя из своих моральных принципов, согласуя со своей совестью.

При изучении развития морального сознания у детей анализировались, их суждения по поводу проступков сверстников-героев рассказов. Дети сравнивали «рассказы о двух проявлениях оплошности». [4, с. 108-109].

Развитие морального сознания начинается с 4 лет. В старшем дошкольном возрасте дети воспринимают правила поведения и моральные нормы как реальные нерушимые условия жизни, которые необходимо следовать при любых обстоятельствах.

Представления об относительности норм и правил поведения появляются у ребёнка начиная с 7 лет. Младший школьник осознает, что правила создаются людьми и становятся результатом всеобщей договоренности; при изменении обстоятельств их могут изменить.

Считается, что по мере взросления нравственное развитие становится все менее зависимым от возраста. Ребёнок может знать, как правильно себя вести, но по какой-то причине. [5, с. 46].

Развитие морального сознания, приобретение этических представлений-важная сторона развития личности в детстве.

Воспитательное пространство включает в своё содержание все основные материально-производственные и научно-технические достижения.

Школьник проживает часть жизни в школьном доме, и все характеристики этого дома, считаются объектом его заботы, то есть, школьник должен содействовать укреплению, сохранению этих характеристик.

Решающим условием нравственного воспитания является высокая культура педагогического коллектива, управляющего воспитательным процессом. Педагог легко и просто будет совершать с детьми ежемоментное восхождение на уровень культуры [8, с. 89].

Выбор методов нравственного воспитания во многом зависит от возраста учащихся и их жизненного опыта. Характер методов нравственного воспитания изменяется и в зависимости от развития детского коллектива. Если коллектив еще не

сформирован, воспитатель предъявляет в твердой и категоричной форме требования ко всем детям. Как только заметную роль в коллективе начинает играть актив учащихся, методика работы должна меняться.

В связи с этим процесс нравственного развития младших школьников необходимо рассматривать как постепенное достижение гармонии и психолого-педагогического единства развивающего действия эмоционально-чувственной и интеллектуально-рациональной сфер личности, обеспечивающее накопление, осознание и развитие школьником эмоционально пережитых и личностно принятых этических норм поведения. Логика данного процесса предполагает направленность на совершенствование и реализацию всей совокупности моральных ориентиров и ценностно-значимых смыслов жизнедеятельности человека в образе жизни школьника.

Важнейшим психолого-педагогическим принципом организации процесса нравственного воспитания является последовательная поэтапность. Внутри каждого этапа также заложены в соответствии со стоящими задачами принципы и методические подходы, обеспечивающие его воспитание.

В младших классах часто используется рассказ на этическую тему. Воздействуя на чувства, рассказ помогает воспитанникам понять и усвоить смысл моральных оценок и норм поведения. Рассказ сопровождается иллюстрациями, которыми могут стать произведения живописи, художественные фотографии, изделия народных умельцев. Усиливает его восприятие хорошо подобранное музыкальное сопровождение. Эмоциональное воздействие окружающей обстановки должно соответствовать замыслу и содержанию рассказа. Рассказ обязательно должен переживаться слушателями.

Разъяснение - метод эмоционально-словесного воздействия. Для младших школьников применяются элементарные приемы и средства разъяснения: «поступать нужно так», «все так делают» и т.п.

Разъяснение применяется для того, чтобы сформировать или закрепить новое моральное качество или форму поведения, для выработки правильного отношения воспитанников к определенному поступку, который уже совершен.

В начальной школе, как известно, очень эффективно использование игровых методов, что помогает обогатить сознание ребенка нравственными представлениями, соотнести их с соответствующими словами-понятиями, преподать опыт отношений, отвечающий правилам нравственности [7, с. 75].

В нашем исследовании педагогические условия воспитания нравственного воспитания как общечеловеческой ценности мы рассматриваем как совокупность необходимых, обязательных обстоятельств, оказывающих существенное влияние на повышение уровня сформированности нравственного отношения младших школьников к общественно полезному труду.

Первым педагогическим условием является разработка и реализация программы методической помощи педагогу по воспитанию нравственного отношения младших школьников как общечеловеческой ценности. Выделяя данное педагогическое условие, мы руководствовались следующими теоретическими положениями:

– во-первых, в современном социуме возросла потребность в учителе, способном совершенствовать содержание своей деятельности посредством критического, творческого его осмысления и применения достижений науки и передового педагогического опыта ;

– во-вторых, педагог должен уметь отбирать целесообразные методы и формы воспитательной работы [6, с. 56].

Формы воспитания - это внешнее выражение совместной деятельности воспитанников и воспитателей по решению воспитательных задач [5, с. 102].

В современной школе учитель воплощает в себе сразу же несколько важных ролей, таких как учитель, воспитатель, сценарист и режиссер. Урок по воспитанию духовно-нравственного воспитания можно рассматривать, как небольшой спектакль, в котором каждому ученику должна быть выделена своя роль. Такая постановка урока позволит учителю использовать новые технологии и развить коммуникативные навыки учащихся.

Наиболее перспективными являются инновационные технологии, связанные с различными формами интерактивного обучения, проектной деятельностью, нестандартными уроками. Одной из обновленной формой работы по формированию социокультурного пространства является волонтерское движение, которое в последние годы набирает масштабность и уже показывает свои позитивные результаты. Волонтерское движение в школе позволяет ученикам утвердить идеи добра, красоты, духовного и физического совершенствования; показывает преимущества здорового образа жизни; создает условия для того, чтобы среди учеников уменьшился уровень потребления алкоголя, табакокурения и т.д.; сплачивает коллектив и объединяет учеников по интересам [6, с. 89].

Средства воспитания - это относительно независимые источники формирования личности, посредники между воспитателем и воспитанником. Средства нравственного воспитания можно объединить в несколько групп. Художественная литература, изобразительное искусство, музыка, кино, диафильмы и др. включены нами в группу художественных средств. Также средством нравственного воспитания является природа, которая дает возможность вызывать у детей гуманные чувства, желание заботиться о тех, кто слабее, защищать их и способствует формированию у ребенка уверенности в себе. Еще одним средством нравственного воспитания является собственная деятельность детей: игра, труд, учение, художественная деятельность. Особое место отводится общению, которое лучше всего выполняет задачи корректировки представлений о морали и воспитании чувств и отношений. Средством нравственного воспитания может быть вся та атмосфера, в которой живет ребенок. Окружающая ребенка обстановка активизирует весь механизм нравственного воспитания и влияет на формирование определенных нравственных качеств [9, с. 71-72].

Таким образом, можно считать что, в начальной школе для воспитания и обучения детей на первом месте стоит - игровой метод, который способствует формированию тех сторон психики, от которых впоследствии будет зависеть успешность его социальной практики.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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Аннотация: одной из основных целей высшего профессионального образования является подготовка профессиональных специалистов. Для подготовки будущих специалистов с необходимым уровнем профессиональной компетентности в условиях современного информационного общества от образовательных учреждений требуется создания современных образовательных сред, способствующих подготовке опытных, креативных и инновационных специалистов.

Ключевые слова: современные технологии, компьютеризация, использование оборудования и технологий, программа компьютеризации, технические навыки, традиционное обучение, инновационная технология, учебный процесс.

В современном, стремительно развивающемся мире невозможно представить деятельность и развитие сферы образования без использования современных информационно-коммуникационных средств и технологий. Как показывают многочисленные исследования, все возрастающий объем информации, используемой в образовании, должен базироваться на едином источнике и обрабатываться современным способом. В этих условиях сфера образования не может быть эффективной без использования современных средств и методов обработки, передачи и представления электронной информации [5,с.66].

Государственная политика в сфере образования направлена на использование информационных технологий в общеобразовательных учреждениях, повышение уровня и качества образования в соответствии с международными стандартами, создание единой цифровой базы электронных образовательных материалов, целью является развитие современной материально-технической базы общеобразовательных учреждений путем их регулярного переоснащения современным оборудованием и технологиями, создание единого информационного портала сферы образования республики.

Оснащение образовательных учреждений техническим оборудованием, начиная со второй ступени образования, позволит учащимся и преподавателям получать доступ к содержательным и эффективным веб-ресурсам. Для эффективной работы педагогов общеобразовательных учреждений необходимо подключение локальной сети.

Информатизация образовательных учреждений - процесс изменения содержания, методов и форм организации образования обучающихся при переходе к образованию с использованием инновационных технологий. В рамках реформирования

образовательного процесса, обновления его содержания, методов и форм организации учебного процесса возникает необходимость в сочетании электронных материалов с традиционными средствами обучения [5,с.67].

Электронные учебно-методические материалы должны разрабатываться на основе современных технологий. Внедрение таких современных учебно-методических материалов в учебный процесс общеобразовательных учреждений позволит обеспечить эффективное использование компьютерных и коммуникационных технологий.

Президент Республики Таджикистан Эмомали Рахмон практически во всех своих посланиях Маджлиси Оли уделяет этому вопросу первостепенное внимание и неоднократно подчеркивает, что «учитель не имеет права на ошибки в процессе обучения и воспитания». Почему? Потому что «судьба будущего поколения, которое будет формировать и развивать государство и общество, находится в их руках». С таким упором и руководством он поручил дальнейшее повышение квалификации и профессионализма учителей. Поэтому им следует проходить переподготовку, курсы повышения квалификации, изучать языки и осваивать современные технологии.

Повышение квалификации учителей включает в себя не только обучение работе с компьютером, но и освоение инновационных методов преподавания предметов. В современных условиях учителя уделяют особое внимание образовательным технологиям. Педагогическая технология связана с системным подходом к образованию и охватывает все аспекты и элементы педагогической системы от начала до конца.

Поскольку, начиная с 2018 года, по поручениям и указаниям Главы государства, процесс оснащения образовательных учреждений современным учебным оборудованием и технологиями должен быть организован более качественно. Стоит отметить, что для повышения квалификации педагогических кадров были скорректированы сроки проведения курсов в период зимних каникул учеников.

Конечно, цель всего этого - воспитать поколение, которое, наряду с современными знаниями, должно расти в духе национального самосознания, патриотизма и патриотической гордости. В связи с этим мы, учителя, стремимся внести свой ценный вклад в развитие молодого поколения, которое будет формировать будущее нашей любимой Родины, совершенствуя свой профессионализм и педагогическое мастерство.

В настоящее время в нашей стране происходят существенные изменения в национальной политике образования. Одной из задач современной школы становится раскрытие потенциала всех участников педагогического процесса, предоставление им возможностей проявления творческих способностей.

Обучение – это двусторонний процесс. Деятельность учителя обычно называют преподаванием, а деятельность ученика – учением. Учение же не только процесс овладения тем, что дано преподаванием, это сложный процесс познавательной деятельности, в котором происходит освоение обобщённого опыта, накопленного человечеством в виде знаний, это и приобретение индивидуального опыта познания при помощи самостоятельного оперирования знаниями, овладения необходимыми действиями и способами [4с.34].

В традиционном обучении ведущую роль играет учитель. Процесс познания учащихся протекает в совместной деятельности с учителем, под его руководством. Учитель направляет этот процесс в соответствии с возрастными возможностями и особенностями учащихся, он систематизирует, конкретизирует содержание обучения,

придаёт логическое обоснование знаниям, которым овладевают учащиеся, он изыскивает наиболее рациональные пути вооружения своих учеников умениями, нужными в самостоятельном познании, вырабатывает навыки [4с.36].

В настоящее время в образовательном процессе используются не только традиционные, но и инновационные технологии. Нововведения, или инновации характерны для любой профессиональной деятельности человека и поэтому, естественно, становятся предметом изучения, анализа и внедрения. Инновации сами по себе не возникают, они являются результатом научных поисков, передового педагогического опыта отдельных учителей и целых коллективов. Этот процесс не может быть стихийным, он нуждается в управлении [1с.26].

Понятие “инновация“ в переводе с латинского языка означает “обновление, новшество или изменение“. Термины “инновации в образовании“ и “педагогические инновации“, употребляемые как синонимы, были научно обоснованы и введены в категориальный аппарат педагогики.

Инновации разрабатываются и проводятся работниками и организациями системы образования и науки [1с.27].

Содержательная структура инновационного процесса предполагает рождение, разработку и освоение новшеств в обучении, воспитательной работе, организации учебно-воспитательного процесса, в управлении школой и т.д. В свою очередь каждый компонент этой структуры имеет своё сложное строение. Так, инновационный процесс в обучении может предполагать нововведения в методах, формах, приёмах, средствах (то есть в технологии), в содержании образования или в его целях, условиях и пр.

Компьютерные технологии не только помогают организовать учебный процесс с использованием игровых методов, но и получить более сильную обратную связь. Средства мультимедиа позволяют обеспечить эффективную организацию процесса обучения.

Проектная деятельность также является технологией активизации учебно-познавательной активности. Этому способствует высокая самостоятельность учащихся в процессе подготовки проекта. Инновационные технологии в преподавании – это новые методы общения с учениками, позволяющие ученикам самоутвердиться. А самоутверждение – это путь к правильному выбору своей профессии.

Необходимо, чтобы традиционные и инновационные технологии обучения были в постоянной взаимосвязи и дополняли друг друга. Эти два понятия должны существовать на одном уровне.

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ENHANCING VOCABULARY RETENTION THROUGH CONTEXTUAL LEARNING IN INTERMEDIATE EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: The article “Enhancing Vocabulary Retention Through Contextual Learning in Intermediate EFL Classrooms” examines how contextual learning helps intermediate EFL learners acquire and retain new vocabulary more effectively. It argues that vocabulary should be learned through meaningful situations rather than simple memorization. The paper explores strategies such as using real-life contexts, stories, and reading passages to make vocabulary learning more engaging and lasting. It also highlights how contextual learning improves comprehension, recall, and active use of words in communication. The study concludes that applying contextual methods in EFL classrooms increases learner motivation and promotes long-term vocabulary retention.

Key words: contextual learning, vocabulary retention, intermediate EFL learners, language acquisition, communicative approach, meaningful context, active learning

Vocabulary learning is the lifeblood of language development and the bridge between comprehension and communication. For learners beyond the earliest stages, vocabulary instruction needs to move away from lists and isolated translation and toward richly textured encounters with words that mirror how language is used in real life. When learners meet words embedded in meaningful contexts, their minds create connections, associations, and usage patterns that are far more resilient than those produced by rote memorization. This article explores how contextual learning can be harnessed in classrooms where learners are at an intermediate stage of English acquisition, offering a careful account of the theoretical underpinnings, the classroom realities, the pedagogical approaches that produce durable learning, and the practical choices teachers can make to design lessons that lead to active, long lasting lexical knowledge.

Practical classroom practice begins with careful selection. Not every word in a text needs instructional attention. Teachers aim to prioritize vocabulary that is useful, frequent enough to justify teaching, relevant to learners' needs, and teachable through context. For intermediate learners, emphasis often falls on multiword units, collocations, and functional vocabulary that supports fluency rather than rare specialized terms. Authentic materials are a rich source of such items: adapted articles, short stories, interviews, and filmed segments provide natural environments where target vocabulary appears with natural partners and punctuation. When authentic input is too dense or lexically heavy, graded texts and well-designed adaptations preserve contextual integrity while remaining accessible. [1]

Assessment practices also need alignment with contextual principles. If tests favor decontextualized recognition, teaching will follow and contextual methods will be marginalized. Formative assessment that samples productive use in communicative tasks, portfolios that collect pieces of writing and recordings of speaking, and self-assessment that encourages learners to reflect on how comfortably they can use new words in real situations are all more consistent with contextual learning. Assessments that require paraphrase,

contextualized gap fills, or short-spoken tasks supply both evidence of learning and further practice opportunities. Teacher talk and classroom interaction patterns shape the effectiveness of contextual vocabulary instruction. A teacher who dominates the interaction and reduces opportunities for learners to negotiate meaning inadvertently lowers the depth of processing. Conversely, teachers who structure pair and group tasks in which learners have to clarify, confirm, and defend lexical choices create high quality opportunities for elaboration. Peer correction and collaborative editing serve the dual purposes of recycling vocabulary and offering immediate feedback, which helps to consolidate form-meaning links. Learner autonomy is a vital complement to classroom contextualization. Even the most skillful design is limited by the amount of exposure any single class can provide. Encouraging learners to seek additional contextual input outside class multiplies opportunities for meaningful encounters. Strategies training that teaches learners how to notice, how to exploit context clues, how to use digital concordancers, and how to keep a dynamic lexical notebook, makes out-of-class engagement more productive. A lexical notebook designed around contexts rather than isolated translations, where each entry contains a sentence from reading or listening, a paraphrase, a collocation list, and a self-created example, becomes a tool for both storage and active retrieval.

Challenges to contextual vocabulary instruction are real but surmountable. Time pressure, large classes, and exam driven curricula can push teachers toward more economical methods like list learning. Yet even within constrained settings, contextual principles can be embedded. Short activities that require authentic use, careful selection of a few teachable items per lesson rather than exhaustive coverage of every unfamiliar word, and the use of homework assignments that recycle words in a variety of forms create a syllabus that respects both practical limits and cognitive realities. Teachers who reframe the goal from covering many words superficially to building deep knowledge of a smaller set will find that learners subsequently acquire new vocabulary more rapidly and reliably because they have stronger analytical skills and more robust lexical scaffolding. The social and affective atmosphere of the classroom influences retention as well. Learners who are anxious about making mistakes will avoid risky language use and thereby deprive themselves of the rehearsal opportunities that consolidate vocabulary. Contextual tasks framed as low stakes, exploratory, and collaborative reduce anxiety and encourage experimentation. Stories and role play that allow learners to inhabit safe, imaginative roles can lower inhibition while still requiring the deployment of target words in communicative situations.

Materials design for contextual learning benefits from a few guiding principles. Texts should be chosen for their potential to offer repeated, varied, and meaningful instances of key vocabulary. Sentences and paragraphs that showcase collocations and that present target items in natural frames are especially useful. Adaptations are acceptable when they preserve the essential contextual cues that make the item interpretable. Visuals, charts, and timelines that accompany texts are not mere decoration; they create extra retrieval cues and allow learners to anchor abstract words to concrete representations. Tasks that require learners to manipulate and produce language based on the text rather than merely answer comprehension questions provide the deeper processing that supports retention. [2]

A narrative account of a lesson can illuminate how these principles operate in practice. Imagine a class that explores a short personal narrative about a traveler who faces an unexpected disruption. The lesson begins with a brief prompt that asks learners to recall a time when their plans changed at the last moment, sparking personal connection. Learners work first in pairs to explain the meanings of unfamiliar items using surrounding sentences, paraphrase challenging lines, and highlight collocations. The teacher then models how to take

one highlighted sentence and transform it into a short-spoken retelling, showing how word choice affects tone and clarity. Pairs plan a brief role play where they must re-enact a similar disruption and negotiate solutions, deliberately using the set of highlighted vocabulary. A short writing homework asks learners to compose an email explaining a change in plans, again prompting transfer of the vocabulary into a different genre.

Professional development for teachers is a necessary ingredient for effective contextual vocabulary teaching. Many teachers have been trained in traditional approaches and may be uncertain about how to orchestrate discovery tasks, how to design tasks that elicit authentic language use, or how to assess depth of lexical knowledge. Collaborative planning, observation cycles, and shared analysis of student work are practical ways to build capacity. Reflective practice encourages teachers to examine which activities prompt genuine lexical uptake and which merely create short term recall. Over time, teachers who adopt contextual methods report that learners become more independent, more willing to take lexical risks, and more adept at inferring meaning from use.

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THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING (CLT) IN DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF UZBEK LEARNERS AT SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. This paper examines the role of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in helping learners develop communicative competence in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Unlike traditional methods such as the Grammar-Translation Method

(GTM) or the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM), CLT focuses on fluency, interaction, and meaningful use of the target language. The article presents the historical background of CLT, its principles, advantages, challenges, and classroom practices. It concludes that CLT is one of the most effective approaches to teaching English, especially in contexts where communicative competence is the main goal.

Keywords: Communicative Language Teaching, communicative competence, EFL, ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida, methodology, second language acquisition.

The teaching of English has gone through different stages, starting from grammar-focused methods to more communicative ones. For many years, the Grammar-Translation Method was dominant, but it mainly helped students read texts and translate sentences without developing real speaking skills. Later, the Audio-Lingual Method became popular by emphasizing drills and repetition. However, this method also did not lead to natural communication.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) appeared in the 1970s as a reaction to these traditional methods. The main purpose of CLT is not only to teach grammar or vocabulary but to help learners use English effectively in real communication. This article explores the background, principles, and effectiveness of CLT in developing communicative competence.

The concept of communicative competence was first introduced by Dell Hymes (1972). He argued that knowledge of language is not only about grammar, but also about its use in social contexts[2]. Later, Canale and Swain (1980) described communicative competence as a combination of four components:

1. Grammatical competence, which is about knowledge of grammar and vocabulary.
2. Sociolinguistic competence describes understanding how to use language appropriately in different situations.
3. Discourse competence is about the ability to connect sentences into a meaningful conversation.
4. Strategic competence implies the ability to use strategies to overcome communication problems [1].

Richards and Rodgers (2014) explain that CLT is based on these ideas and focuses on interaction, authentic communication, and student-centered learning[3]. Consequently, the principles of CLT are worth discussing:

- The main goal of language teaching is communicative competence.
- Fluency is sometimes more important than accuracy. Mistakes are accepted as part of the learning process.
- Activities should be meaningful and connected to real life.
- The classroom should be student-centered, with the teacher acting as a facilitator.
- Pair work and group work are encouraged to increase interaction.

Teachers who use CLT design activities that involve real communication and active participation. Examples include:

- Role plays (e.g., ordering food in a restaurant, asking for directions).
- Interviews and surveys among classmates.
- Discussions and debates about everyday topics.
- Games and problem-solving tasks that require teamwork.

Such activities help Uzbek learners not only practise grammar and vocabulary of the English language at secondary school, but also acquire pronunciation, intonation, and cultural aspects of communication in the English context. As most educators admit CLT to be a more dynamic and interactive (Canale & Swain) approach in second language acquisition, its implementation in the Uzbek classroom presented successful communication of students on

a wide range of topics, thus encouraging creativity and free expression of English, which is generally hard to achieve relying on translation, memorization, repetition, and drilling. Observation of English lessons showed that the use of CLT has shifted learning from accuracy-centered to fluency-centered, thus making CLT especially effective in preparing students in Uzbekistan for real-life communication.

In conclusion, CLT represents one of the most influential methods in modern English language teaching in Uzbekistan. By focusing on real communication and meaningful activities it helps Uzbek learners develop communicative competence. Although there are challenges in its application, especially in contexts where exams dominate, CLT remains an effective approach for preparing students to use English confidently in real-life situations.

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AN ISSUE ON TESTING AND ASSESSMENT FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF EFL CLASSROOM

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Abstract: This article explores key issues in testing and assessment within the EFL classroom context. It highlights the challenges teachers face in balancing formative and summative assessments to accurately measure students' language proficiency. The study emphasizes the importance of validity, reliability, and fairness in test design and implementation. Additionally, it discusses how assessment practices influence learners' motivation, classroom participation, and overall achievement. The article concludes by suggesting strategies for creating more learner-centered and authentic assessment approaches in EFL education.

Key words: EFL classroom, language assessment, formative and summative testing, validity and reliability, learner motivation, authentic assessment, language proficiency.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola EFL (xorijiy til sifatida ingliz tili) sinfida test va baholash masalalarining asosiy jihatlarini o'rganadi. Unda o'qituvchilarning talabalar til kompetensiyasini aniq o'lchash uchun formatif va summativ baholash turlarini muvozanatlashtirishda duch keladigan qiyinchiliklari yoritiladi. Tadqiqot testlarni tuzish va amalga oshirishda ishonchlilik, haqqoniylik va adolatlilik tamoyillarining ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, maqolada baholash amaliyotining o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi, sinfdagi ishtiroki va umumiy yutuqlariga ta'siri muhokama qilinadi. Maqola yakunida EFL ta'limida o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan va autentik baholash yondashuvlarini yaratish bo'yicha strategiyalar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: EFL sinfi, tilni baholash, formatif va summativ testlar, ishonchlilik va haqqoniylik, o'quvchi motivatsiyasi, autentik baholash, til kompetensiyasi.

The organization of effective communication among EFL students is a subject matter of all methodologies in language teaching. The use of Bloom's Taxonomy in the English classroom is an innovative way for EFL teachers to create educational materials for effective

planning and assessing EFL students' language skills. A psychologist investigating cognitive skills, Benjamin Bloom, in his works focused on aligning educational goals to promote higher forms of thinking [Nurmatova & Altun 2023, 382]. He described a systematic classification of learning objectives and their arrangement into six hierarchical levels each representing a different cognitive skill [4], comparing to the revised taxonomy that includes verbs and actions rather than nouns [Krathwohl 2002,213].

Krathwohl states that taxonomy is a hierarchy of levels and declaration of explicit educational objectives. Moreover, he adds that the successiveness of levels presupposes mastering of levels as they are approached by their complexity.

As an educational framework, Bloom's taxonomy is aimed at differentiating learning with the implementing levels of cognition. The integration of the ascending levels of complexity ensures EFL teachers to adapt the learning materials to the needs of their students.

Bloom's Taxonomy is divided into six levels

1. Remembering: Recalling basic facts like vocabulary and grammar rules.
2. Understanding: Comprehending the meaning of words, sentences, and texts.
3. Applying: Using language knowledge in real situations.
4. Analyzing: Breaking down language into smaller parts to understand how it works.
5. Evaluating: Making judgments about how language is used based on certain standards.
6. Creating: Producing original language through speaking or writing.

These levels help students gradually build from basic understanding to more advanced thinking. The revised version of Bloom's Taxonomy, by Anderson and Krathwohl (2001), focuses on active learning through actions like recalling, applying, and creating [1,p.395].

Language learning is a cognitive process that benefits from Bloom's structured approach. It supports the development of the four main language skills at every level of the taxonomy. According to Harmer (2007), learners develop from simple recall to more advanced, critical language use as they move through these stages [5].

1. Remembering: In the early stages, learners memorize basic vocabulary and grammar. Flashcards, quizzes, and repetition exercises help students remember the key building blocks of the language [10,p.51].

2. Understanding: Students then understand how words and grammar work together. Exercises on developing reading skills, listening skills enhancing activities, and discussions help students grasp meanings in context [6,p.180].

3. Applying: At this stage, learners start using their knowledge practically, such as in role-playing or writing activities. These exercises help them apply language to real-world situations [9,p.63].

4. Analyzing: Students analyze language structures to understand more complex texts or conversations. This helps them think critically about how language is used [Brown 2007,59].

5. Evaluating: At this level, learners evaluate language, such as by critiquing others' speeches or writing essays that require careful reasoning [2].

6. Creating: Students create original content like stories or presentations, which encourages them to experiment with language [5,p.98].

EFL teachers who practiced Bloom's Taxonomy in the classroom marked the activities that involved all six levels of learning based on the degree of difficulty. The results showed that the students of higher educational level admitted testing and assessment by the use of Bloom's taxonomy were able to promote their individual growth while guiding the students from simple recall to more complex thinking, helping them build a well-rounded understanding of the language.

The analysis of students' performance based on Bloom's Taxonomy marked the following progress in the English language teaching and learning:

1. Structured learning: It provided a clear learning path from memorization to creative use of language in the English Language acquisition and experience [1,p.250].

2. Balanced skill development: It ensured that lessons cover all key language skills, listening, speaking, reading, and writing [9].

3. Active learning: By focusing on higher-order thinking, it encouraged students to participate actively, which helps them retain what they learn for the long term [3,p.491].

4. Critical thinking: It helped students develop critical thinking skills by analyzing and evaluating language [5,p.69], thus adapting the students to developing lifelong learning.

In conclusion, Bloom's Taxonomy is a powerful tool for teaching languages and guiding students through different levels of learning from developing the critical and creative abilities to a deeper understanding of language and its confident use in real-world situations.

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DEVELOPING L2 LISTENING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article explores the importance of listening for specific information in second language (L2) learning and teaching. It discusses major challenges learners face when developing this subskill and presents effective strategies teachers can use to support them. The paper emphasizes the role of explicit instruction, metacognitive awareness, and scaffolded practice in improving learners' listening comprehension. It concludes with several practical classroom recommendations for teachers and suggestions for further study.

Keywords: listening comprehension, L2 learning, specific information, scaffolding, metacognitive strategies

Listening is one of the most essential skills in language learning, and among its subskills, listening for specific information plays a particularly vital role. This type of listening involves focusing on concrete details such as names, numbers, dates, or specific facts within spoken language, which are crucial for real-life situations like understanding announcements, following directions, or answering comprehension questions during exams. Many learners struggle with this skill because they attempt to understand every word instead of focusing on key information. Research indicates that rapid speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, and a lack of effective listening strategies are major obstacles [1]. Therefore, teachers must

guide learners in developing techniques that allow them to identify essential details efficiently. Listening for specific information differs from global listening, which focuses on the overall meaning of a text. In detail-oriented listening, learners must attend to precise elements such as time, location, or quantity. However, they often face difficulties due to the fast pace of speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, or the inability to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant information. To address these challenges, teachers can train learners to predict what they will hear, identify signal words such as first, next, and finally, and take brief notes of key points. Effective teaching of this subskill requires a combination of explicit strategy instruction, scaffolded practice, and reflective learning.

Explicit strategy instruction involves teachers modeling listening processes—previewing questions, predicting answers, and checking comprehension—to help students approach listening tasks strategically. Scaffolded listening tasks provide guided support through techniques such as dividing recordings into shorter parts, replaying difficult segments, or using visual aids like charts and diagrams. These methods help learners manage cognitive load and focus on critical details. Pre-listening activities, such as discussing the topic or reviewing key vocabulary, prepare students for what they will hear and activate relevant background knowledge. During listening, students can focus on specific elements such as names, dates, or numbers while using shorthand notes to capture details efficiently. Post-listening reflection allows learners to analyze which strategies were effective and encourages metacognitive awareness through discussions or short written reflections. Despite these methods, learners often report recurring challenges such as fast speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, memory limitations, distractors, and variations in pronunciation. Native speakers' rapid or reduced speech forms can make comprehension difficult, while unknown words may divert attention from the target details. In addition, keeping multiple pieces of information in working memory can overwhelm learners, particularly when dealing with long or complex passages. To overcome these difficulties, repetition, contextual learning, and gradual exposure to authentic materials are essential for improving listening proficiency. Teachers play a key role in helping students overcome these barriers and enhance their listening skills. Research and classroom experience suggest several effective techniques, including teaching prediction strategies, providing guided worksheets, using short listening materials before authentic ones, allowing multiple listening to build confidence, and incorporating reflection activities such as listening journals. Moreover, offering feedback on both results and strategy use helps learners refine their approach and develop independence. These pedagogical practices not only improve comprehension but also promote learner autonomy and confidence. Although many strategies have proven effective, no single approach works equally well for all learners. Success depends on individual factors such as proficiency level, motivation, and exposure to English outside the classroom. Future research could explore how digital listening tools, including adaptive learning apps and AI-based listening platforms, can personalize instruction and meet diverse learner needs. In conclusion, listening for specific information is a practical and essential subskill in second language learning. To help learners succeed, teachers must provide explicit strategy instruction, scaffolded tasks, and opportunities for metacognitive reflection. Through consistent practice, guided feedback, and exposure to authentic listening situations, students develop the confidence and accuracy needed to become effective listeners capable of handling academic and everyday communication.

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TIL O‘RGANISHNING XUSUSIYATLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til o‘rganish jarayonida o‘quvchilarning individual, psixologik va pedagogik xususiyatlari, til o‘rganish samaradorligini oshirishda o‘qituvchining roli, motivatsiya, ta‘lim metodlari va muhit omillarining ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, chet tilini o‘rganishda kommunikativ yondashuv, mustaqil fikrlash va madaniy tafakkurning shakllanishi masalalariga ham e‘tibor qaratilgan. Maqola zamonaviy ta‘lim tamoyillariga asoslangan holda tahliliy tarzda yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: til o‘rganish, motivatsiya, metodika, pedagogik yondashuv, kommunikativ kompetensiya, ta‘lim muhiti, shaxsiy xususiyatlar.

Abstract: This article analyzes the individual, psychological, and pedagogical characteristics of learners in the process of language acquisition. It examines the teacher’s role in enhancing learning effectiveness, as well as the importance of motivation, teaching methods, and environmental factors. Special attention is given to communicative approaches, the development of independent thinking, and the formation of cultural awareness in foreign language learning. The article is presented in an analytical manner, based on the principles of modern education.

Keywords: language learning, motivation, methodology, pedagogical approach, communicative competence, learning environment, personal characteristics

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются индивидуальные, психологические и педагогические особенности учащихся в процессе изучения языка. Рассматривается роль преподавателя в повышении эффективности обучения, а также значение мотивации, методов преподавания и факторов образовательной среды. Особое внимание уделено коммуникативному подходу, развитию самостоятельного мышления и формированию культурного сознания при изучении иностранного языка. Статья изложена в аналитическом формате на основе современных принципов образования.

Ключевые слова: изучение языка, мотивация, методика, педагогический подход, коммуникативная компетенция, образовательная среда, личностные особенности.

Til insonning tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi va madaniyatini ifodalovchi eng muhim vositadir. Tilni o‘rganish jarayoni nafaqat grammatik qoidalarni o‘zlashtirish, balki madaniy, psixologik va ijtimoiy omillarni ham o‘z ichiga oladi. Pedagogik nuqtayi nazardan til

o'rganish o'quvchi shaxsining rivojlanishiga, tafakkurini kengaytirishga va muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shu sababli til o'rganishdagi xususiyatlarni o'rganish bugungi ta'lim tizimi uchun muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega [1].

Til o'rganish - bu o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi o'zaro faol ta'sir jarayoni bo'lib, u tilni amaliy qo'llash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yo'naltiriladi. O'qituvchi bu jarayonda nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki motivatsiya beruvchi, yo'naltiruvchi va psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlovchi shaxs sifatida ishtirok etadi [2]. Til o'rgatishda samarali metodlarni tanlash, darsni o'yin, muloqot, loyiha yoki muhokama shaklida tashkil etish o'quvchilarni faol ishtirokchi qiladi [3].

Har bir o'quvchining tilni o'zlashtirish tezligi, eslab qolish darajasi va e'tiborini jamlash qobiliyati turlicha bo'ladi. Shuning uchun o'qituvchi individual yondashuvni qo'llashi zarur. Yosh xususiyatlari, temperament, o'quvchining o'ziga ishonchi va ichki motivatsiyasi til o'rganish samaradorligiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Masalan, extrovert o'quvchilar muloqotda faol bo'lishsa, introvertlar yozma mashqlar orqali yaxshiroq natija ko'rsatishlari mumkin [4].

Til o'rganishda motivatsiya - eng muhim jabhalardan biri. Ichki motivatsiya (qiziqish, o'zini rivojlantirish istagi) va tashqi motivatsiya (imtihon, baho, ishga joylashish ehtiyoji) o'quv jarayonini harakatga keltiradi va tezroq natijaga erishish uchun muhim qadam bo'lib xizmat qiladi. O'qituvchi o'quvchilarda ichki motivatsiyani uyg'ota olgan taqdirdagina o'rganish jarayoni samarali kechadi [5].

Til o'rganish - bu murakkab, ammo ijodiy jarayon. U nafaqat bilim olishni, balki shaxsiy rivojlanish, muloqot madaniyati va tafakkur kengayishini, o'zga millat mintaleti bilan tanishish imkonini ham ta'minlaydi. O'qituvchi til o'rganishdagi shaxsiy, psixologik va metodik xususiyatlarni inobatga olgan holda darsni tashkil etsa, natijalar o'ylangani kabi yuqori va samarali bo'ladi. Har bir o'quvchining individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish, motivatsiyani uyg'otish, madaniy qadriyatlarni singdirish - samarali til o'rganishning kaliti.

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TILGA MUNOSABAT - ELGA MUNOSABAT

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tiliga bo'lgan e'tibor, u duch kelayotgan muammolar, uning hayotimizdagi o'rni va xalqimizning bu muammolarga bo'lgan munosabati, tengdoshlarimizning kompyuter asridagi savodxonlik darajasi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tilga munosabat, millat ruhi, peshtaxta yozuvlari, afishalar imlosi muammosi, ijtimoiy tarmoq, tez yozmoq, qisqa fikr ifodalash, o'quv markaz, tashkilot, Muhammad Yusuf, Alisher Navoiy, turkiy til.

Abstract: This article discusses the attention given to the Uzbek language, the challenges it faces, its role in our daily lives, and society's attitude toward these issues. It also examines the level of literacy among today's youth in the computer age.

Key words: attitude toward language, national spirit, shop signs, spelling problems in advertisements, social networks, fast typing, concise expression, educational centers, organizations, Muhammad Yusuf, Alisher Navoi, Turkic language.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается внимание, уделяемое узбекскому языку, проблемы, с которыми он сталкивается, его место в нашей жизни и отношение общества к этим вопросам. Также анализируется уровень грамотности современной молодежи в эпоху компьютерных технологий.

Ключевые слова: отношение к языку, дух нации, вывески, проблема орфографии в афишах, социальные сети, быстрая печать, краткое выражение мысли, учебные центры, организации, Мухаммад Юсуф, Алишер Навои, тюркский язык.

Til millat ko'zguzi, borligi, birligi, o'tmishi va bugunni aks ettiruvchi muhim omil hisoblanadi. Millat yashasha til ham doimo o'sib rivojlanib boradi¹. Shuning uchun har qanday xalq uning qadr-qimmatini va himoyasi haqida doim o'ylashi va qayg'urishi lozim. Bugungi kunda ona tilimizga bo'layotgan munosabat va uning qay darajada mavqega ega ekanligini kuzatmoqdamiz. Bosqinchi, eng avvalo tilga hujum qiladi. Buni tarix isbotlab turibdi. O'zbek xalqi ham asrlar davomida o'zining tilini va qadriyatlarini asrab avaylab, himoya qilib kelmoqda. Ammo, keyingi yillarda ona tilimiz rivoji yo'lida duch kelayotgan muammolar va unga bo'lgan munosabat hamda tilimizga nisbatan tashqi ta'sirlarlar ko'payayotgani sir emas. Yurtimizda tashkilotlar, muassasalar, korxonalar nomlari, o'quv markazlari, do'konlar peshtaxtalariga yozilgan ajnabiy tildagi nomlanishlar kishining g'ashiga tegar darajada ko'paymoqda. Masalan, "Los Angeles", "IDEAL STUDY" xususiy o'quv markazi, "Element" o'quv markazi, "Real School" o'quv markazlarining nomlanishini ko'rib hayron qolaman, bu joyda nechta ingliz bolasi o'qirgan(?), hammasi o'zbekning farzandlari-ku. Nima, o'quv markaz nomini o'zbekcha yozsa, ilm tolibi kelmay qoladi-mi?.. Ayniqsa, bunday so'zlar imlosini ko'raverib "ko'zi o'rganib" qolgan yoshlarimiz imlosida ham "inglizlashish" bo'y ko'rsatayotganligi xavotirli emasmi? Til, imlo masalasi faqat tilchilarning ishi deb o'ylashning oqibati, meningcha. Peshtaxtalarda o'z ona tilimizda emas boshqa tillardagi nomlanishlarni berayotganimiz ayanchli ahvolga tushib qolganimiz emasmi? Yoki o'z ona tilimizga bo'lgan hurmatimizmi? Biz bunga qanday qarayapmiz? Bunday xato(!)larni to'g'rilab yozishimiz va o'z ona tilimizda nom berishimiz darkor. Ko'chalarda afishalarda yozilgan shiorlarni ham aniq va imloviy xatolarsiz yozishimiz kerakligini ko'rsatmoqda. Zotan til oddiy masala emas!

Qaysiki millat o'z tiliga bo'lgan munosabatini ijobiy tomonga o'zgartirmasa, tildan uzoqlashadi va o'z ona tilidan mahrum bo'ladi. Shuning uchun, ona tilimizni asrab avaylashimiz va uni puxta bilishimiz, dunyo miqyosiga olib chiqish bizning vazifamiz ekanligini unutib qo'ymasligimiz kerak. Millat sifatida jahon maydonida bo'lish uchun o'zbek tilini ko'z qorachug'idek asrash har bir o'zbekning faxrli burchidir. Bugungi kunda yoshlar imlosining sustligiga maktab va oliygohlarda yozma savodxonlikka talab qo'yilmasligi, qolaversa, ijtimoiy tarmoqdan yoshlarimiz-ning noo'rin foydalanishi ham ma'lum darajada ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ular ijtimoiy tarmoqda tez va qisqa yozishga urunib ba'zi so'zlarni bosh harfi va oxirgi harfini yozishmoqda. Masalan, *bilan* so'zini "bn", *sh* harf birikmasini ingliz tilidagi "w" harfi bilan yozishmoqda. Buning oqibatida esa yoshlarimiz o'zining tilida to'g'ri yozishni unutib yubormoqda. Shoirimiz Muhammad Yusufning "Kechir ona tilim" she'rida aytilgandek, o'z tilimizdan kechirim so'raydigan ahvolga kelib qolmadikmi?!

*Sen bo'lmasang nima bizga sillik she'rlar,
Bu dunyoda tili yo'qda dil yo'q derlar,
Bahoiing-ku berib ketgan Alisherlar,
Yuragimning to'ridagi so'lmas gulim
Ona tilim, kechir meni, ona tilim?*

She'rning ushbu to'rtligida tilimiz bo'lmasa mukammal she'rlar ham yaratilmaydi, tili yo'q insonlarda dili ham, qalbi ham bo'lmaydi deydi shoir. Bizning tilimizni buyuk bobokalonimiz Alisher Navoiy adabiy tilining qonun- qoidalarini yuksak darajada ishlab chiqqan, o'sha davrdayoq bu tilning boy va yuksakligini isbotlagan. Har bir insonning dili va tilida o'zining tili oliy darajada turishi lozim.

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O'ZBEK TOVUSHSHUNOSLIGINING AYRIM MUAMMOLARI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilining tovushlar tizimi va imlo me'yorlarining mosligi muhokamasi, tovushlar tizimini mukammal o'rganish ayrim so'zlar etimologiyasini to'g'ri belgilanishiga asos bo'lishi, turkiy tillar tarixida unlilar miqdorining kuzatilishi, undosh tovushlardagi kuchli va kuchsiz talaffuz etilish ma'no farqlashga xizmat qilishi haqida bayon etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: turkiy til, turkiy tillar oilasi, o'zbek tili, tovushlar tizimi, unli va undosh, asos til, etimologik tahlil, singarmonizm qonuniyati, labial singarmonizm, palatal singarmonizm.

Abstract: This article discusses the correspondence between the Uzbek language's sound system and spelling norms, emphasizing that a thorough study of phonetics provides a foundation for correctly determining the etymology of certain words. It also examines the observation of vowel quantity in the history of Turkic languages and explains how the strong and weak pronunciation of consonants contributes to distinguishing meanings.

Keywords: Turkic language, Turkic language family, Uzbek language, sound system, vowels and consonants, root language, etymological analysis, law of synharmonism, labial harmony, palatal harmony.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается соответствие между звуковой системой узбекского языка и нормами орфографии. Подчеркивается, что глубокое изучение фонетической системы служит основой для правильного определения этимологии отдельных слов. Также анализируется количество гласных в истории тюркских языков и показано, как сильное и слабое произношение согласных способствует различению значений.

Ключевые слова: тюркский язык, семья тюркских языков, узбекский язык, звуковая система, гласные и согласные, исходный язык, этимологический анализ, закон сингармонизма, лабиальный сингармонизм, палатальный сингармонизм.

Har bir millatning asosiy belgisi til bo'lib, u insonlararo muloqotning eng muhim va tezkor vositasi sifatida ahamiyatli. "Til millatning borlig'i, uning oyinayi jahonidir"- deya ta'kidlanishi shundandir. O'zbek tilini o'qitishda ta'lim jarayonida tilning tovushlar tizimini o'rganish muhim poydevor bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Fonetika bo'limining mukammal o'zlashtirilishi keyingi bo'limlarda so'zlarning leksik, grammatik ma'nosini aniqlash, turkumlarga ajratish, so'zlarning etimologiyasini belgilashdagi masalalarning to'g'ri hal etilishi uchun asos bo'ladi.

Turkiy tillar tarixida til oilasi uchun turkiy til bobo til – asos til bo'lgan bo'lsa, keying davrlarda o'zbek tili voris – o'zak til vazifasini bajarib kelmoqda. Tilimiz tarixidan ma'lumki, ba'zan ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'zgarishlar tufayli turkiy tillar imlosi bir necha marotaba o'zgarishga uchragan.

Turkiy tilning tarixiy yozma manbalarida turk-run yozuvi oromiy yozuviga asoslangan 22 harfdan iborat bo'lib, uni finikiyaliklar qo'llagan, ulardan arab nobotiyalar qabilasi 22 harf holda qabul qildi va o'z tovushlar tizimini to'liq ifodalash maqsadida 6 ta belgi qo'shdi. Bu belgilarning ayrimlarini nuqtalar bilan bezab, 6 belgi bilan 8 tovushni ifodaladilar, shunday qilib arablarda 28 harfdan iborat alifbo yaratildi. Keyinchalik, arablarning Fors yarim oroliga yurishi natijasida 28 harfdan iborat alifbo fors tiliga kirib keldi. Forslar ham o'z tovushlarini imloda to'liq ifodalash maqsadida 4 ta harf qo'shdi. Bular: "be"- "b" shaklining nuqtalarini ko'paytirib "pe"- "p" belgisini, "jim"- "j" harfiga ikki nuqta qo'shib "chim"- "ch" harfini, "ro"- "r" harfidan "je"- "j" harfini, "kof"- "k" dan "gof"- "g" harfini yasadilar. O'rta Osiyoga arab bosqini tufayli turkiy millatlar ham o'z yozuvlarini o'zgartirishga, arab – eski o'zbek yozuviga o'tishga majbur bo'ldi. VIII asrdan XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmigacha yaratilgan madaniy merosimizning katta qismi shu yozuvda yaratildi. Eramizgacha va eramizda yaratilgan yozma manbalarni o'qish va fanga ma'lum qilish uchun ham grafika tarixini, tarixiy fonetikani o'rganish kun masalasidir.

Turk-run yozuvining 40 dan ortiq shakl(belgi)lari borligi aytiladi. Alifboda unililar soni 4 ta, Enasoy variantida 5 ta¹. Ayrim tilshunos olimlarning ta'kidlashicha tilimiz tarixida 9-16 unli sistemasi ham amal qilgan. Mahmud Koshg'ariy ham dastlab ana shu muammoga duch keldi. Buning boisini, E.Umarov ta'kidlashicha, arab tilida uchta qisqa **fatha-a, kasra-i, zamma-u** va uchta cho'ziq (**alif-a:, vov-u:, yoy-i:**) – jami olti unli mavjudligi, turkiy tillarda esa ular 9 tadan 16 tagacha ekanligi bilan izohlaydi².

Tilshunos olimlar Xudoyberdi Doniyorov, Bosim To'yhiboyev tilga oid asarlarida o'zbek tilining qipchoq dialektida 9 unlilik holati haniz saqlanib kelayotgani, bu xususiyat turkiy tillarning deyarli barchasiga taalluqli bo'lganligi ta'kidlanadi. Fonemalar va ularning yozuvdagi ifodalanish darajasi har doim ham bir xil emas, fonema va harf o'rtasidagi munosabat doim ham mos kelavermaydi. Chunonchi, Mahmud Koshg'ariy ا, و, ي, ه harflari unlini ifodalash bilan birga, birikma shaklida "qalin-ingichkalik" belgisi bilan farq qiluvchi va so'z ma'nosini farqlashga xizmat qiladigan bir necha fonemani ifodalashini qayd etgan. Masalan, **ot** (**o't**) so'zidagi unli qalin talaffuz qilinsa, *o't* (*olov*) ma'nosini, ingichka (**ö** tarzida) talaffuz qilinsa, *devorda va taxtadagi teshikni*, yanada ingichkaroq talaffuz etilsa, *o't qopchasi* ma'nosini anglatishini uqtiradi. Ko'rinadiki, ularning har biri alohida leksema va leksemalarning ma'no tafovutini yuzaga keltirishda fonema muhim o'rin tutadi:

“ **ot** - *o't, olov*; **ot** **tēcä ag'ëz kÿjmäc** – *o't degan bilan og'iz kuymas*; **öt** - [و harfi ingichka (**ö** tarzida) talaffuz etiladi] *devorda va taxtada bo'lgan teshik*; **öt** (و harfi yuqoridagidan ham ingichkaroq talaffuz etiladi) – *achchiqlik, o't* [ö]

qopchasi”³. Har bir xalqning nutq tovushlarini yuzaga keltiruvchi artikulyatsiyasi o‘ziga xos va bu jihat, birinchi navbatda, fonetik jarayonlarda namoyon bo‘ladi. Shuning uchun ham o‘zga tildagi ayrim tovushlarni talaffuz qilishda qiyinchiliklar vujudga kelishi tabiiy hol. Qisqalik, cho‘ziqlik, ingichkalik, yo‘g‘onlik xususiyati unilarga xos, qattiqlik va yumshoqlik xususiyati esa, undoshlarga xosligi leksemalar ma’nosini farqlashda ahamiyatlidir.

Bir tovushning **yumshoq** yoki **qattiq** talaffuzida mas’uliyat bor va u ma’noning farqlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Masalan: كۆك **kök** so‘zidagi **k** qattiq talaffuz etilganda *osmon*, yumshoq talaffuz etilganda esa *rang* ma’nosini berishi qayd etilgan⁴. Tarixiy manbalarda kelgan Ko‘k turk atamasi “osmon turki”, “Tangri turki” ma’nolarini beradi. Binobarin, ushbu tovushning ayrim so‘zlar tarkibida yumshoq yoki qattiq talaffuz etilishi stilistik otenkalarni farqlashga xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham olim quyidagi fikrlarni bayon etgan: “بکچ **bekäch** – *tekinlarning laqabi*. بکچ ارسلان تگین **bekäch arslan tegin** kabi. Bu so‘z yumshoq **k** bilan aytilsa, **bek** so‘zining kichraytirilgani bo‘lib, mehribonlik va achinish ma’nolarini ifoda qiladi. Chunki *amir* ma’nosidagi **bek** so‘zi oxiridagi **k** yumshoq **k** dir”.

Bu stilistik nozikliklar mana bu tahlillarda yana ham oydinroq namoyon bo‘lgan: “سۆگۈتلىك **sögytlyk** – *tolzor*. Oxiri qattiq **k** bilan tugasa, shu ma’noda, agar oxiri yumshoq **g** bilan bitganda, tol egasi ma’nosida qo‘llanadi”. Shuningdek, كۆز چۆچۈك **közchlyk** – *1.xurmacha qilish (yasash) uchun tayyorlangan joy, agar so‘z oxiri yumshoq g bilan bitsa, uning egasi ma’nosini ifodalaydi*. Bu o‘rinda, 1-k “kofi as-sulbat”, 2- k “kofi ar-raqiqa”dir⁵.

Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tilida bu holatni to‘liq anglamagan holda, -li va -lik affekslarining ma’no farqlashi sifatida ta’kidlanmoqda. Vaholangki, -lig va -lik tarzida talqin qilinsa to‘g‘riroq: Sirdaryolik- joyga nisbatan, Sirdaryolig- shaxsga nisbatan qo‘llanilishi maqsadga muvofiq bo‘ladi.

Demak, tilimizning tovushlar tizimini tarixiy ildizlardan boshlab o‘rganish va o‘zlashtirish tildagi qonuniyat va qoidalarning amal qilishidagi farqlanishlarini to‘g‘ri hamda aniq belgilash omili ekan. Fonetmalar o‘zgarishi jarayonlarini to‘g‘ri belgilash ko‘p holatlarda so‘zlar etimologiyasini aniqlashga yordam berishi hozirgi lingvistik tadqiqotlarda ham samara bermoqda.

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PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN THE FIELD OF MEDICINE

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Annotation: This article explores the role of professional language acquisition in the medical field, focusing on the challenges of applying a communicative approach and integrating pedagogical methods tailored to healthcare contexts. It emphasizes the importance of specialized language for effective doctor-patient interaction, medical documentation, and interprofessional communication. The study also highlights current educational practices,

limitations, and potential strategies to improve medical students' and professionals' language proficiency through context-based learning and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Keywords: medical language, communicative approach, pedagogical integration, professional communication, ESP, language in healthcare, medical English

In the modern era of global healthcare and interdisciplinary collaboration, language skills in the medical field have become just as essential as clinical knowledge. Professional medical language is a specialized sub-language that requires clarity, precision, and accuracy. It plays a critical role in patient safety, accurate diagnosis, effective treatment, and international research exchange. For medical students and healthcare workers, mastering the language of medicine is a complex task that involves not only terminology acquisition but also the ability to communicate with patients, colleagues, and institutions in both native and foreign languages - primarily English.

Furthermore, language learners in the medical field often struggle with anxiety and performance pressure. Communicating in a second or foreign language within a clinical environment intensifies this stress, especially when stakes are high. A communicative approach must therefore not only develop linguistic competence but also build confidence and psychological readiness. Activities such as simulated patient interviews, case-based role plays, and peer feedback sessions have been shown to enhance both communication skills and learner motivation.

In summary, the effective teaching and learning of professional language in medicine require a shift from decontextualized, theory-heavy instruction to practical, patient-centered communication training. This shift demands not only methodological innovation but also systemic change in how medical institutions perceive and prioritize language competence. Through communicative pedagogy, contextual relevance, and interdisciplinary collaboration, it is possible to build a generation of healthcare professionals who are not only clinically skilled but also linguistically and culturally competent.

Medical language differs significantly from general language due to its specialized vocabulary, structured syntax, and context-dependent meanings. The traditional approach to teaching medical English or other professional languages has often been limited to memorization of terminology and reading comprehension. However, this method proves insufficient when medical professionals face real-life communication scenarios that require spontaneity, empathy, and adaptability. A more effective strategy is the communicative approach, which emphasizes language use in realistic professional contexts - such as patient interviews, case discussions, and clinical note writing.

Yet, implementing communicative methods in medical education presents certain obstacles. One major challenge is the lack of instructors with dual expertise in both language pedagogy and medical content. Language teachers may not fully grasp clinical concepts, while medical faculty may lack training in teaching methodology. This gap hinders the development of truly integrated, context-specific language programs. Therefore, interdisciplinary collaboration between medical educators and language specialists is vital to create effective curricula.

Moreover, medical education tends to be highly content-heavy, leaving limited time for language training. In many institutions, language learning is still treated as a secondary or supplementary activity, not a core skill. However, communication errors in clinical settings can lead to misdiagnoses, patient dissatisfaction, or even legal consequences - all of which underscore the need for systematic language instruction.

To overcome these issues, context-based learning (CBL) has shown promising results. By embedding language instruction within medical scenarios - such as role-plays,

simulations, and problem-based learning - students gain not only linguistic knowledge but also practical communication skills. For example, using simulated patients during English classes helps learners practice how to explain diagnoses, ask sensitive questions, and give clear instructions. This method bridges the gap between linguistic theory and clinical practice.

In recent years, digital tools have further supported medical language education. Online platforms, mobile apps, video tutorials, and virtual simulations allow for flexible, personalized learning experiences. These technologies also support multimodal learning, which is particularly effective for mastering pronunciation, listening comprehension, and vocabulary in clinical contexts.

Pedagogical integration of medical language learning requires a paradigm shift - treating professional communication as a core component of medical competence. Curricula should incorporate communicative tasks, interdisciplinary teaching teams, and authentic materials sourced from real clinical environments. Moreover, assessment should move beyond written tests to include practical evaluations such as oral exams, patient interviews, and case presentations in English or other target languages.

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IJTIMOYIY TARMOQLARDAGI AKSIOLINGVISTIKA: TIL, QADRIYAT VA VIRTUAL MULOQOTNING O‘ZARO MUNOSABATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi til birliklari orqali qadriyatlarining ifodalanishi, ularning aksiologik mazmun kasb etish jarayoni va virtual muloqotda til vositalarining yangi semantik xususiyat kasb etishi tahlil qilinadi. Aksiolingvistika – til va qadriyat munosabatini o‘rganuvchi yangi yo‘nalish sifatida, internet kommunikatsiyasida paydo bo‘layotgan yangi ma’no qatlamlarini tahlil etishda muhim metodologik asos vazifasini bajaradi. Maqolada o‘zbek tarmoq tilida (xususan, Telegram, Instagram va TikTok platformalarida) ijtimoiy, madaniy va axloqiy qadriyatlarining til orqali ifodalanish usullari ko‘rsatib berilgan. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda qadriyatlarining transformatsiyasi, yangi leksik birliklar va ularning aksio-semantik tabiatiga oid ilmiy kuzatishlar keltiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: aksiolingvistika, qadriyat, ijtimoiy tarmoq, virtual muloqot, internet tili, aksiosemantika, madaniyat, kommunikatsiya.

Abstract: This article analyzes the expression of values through linguistic units in social networks, the process by which they acquire axiological meaning, and the emergence of new semantic features of language in virtual communication. As a new field studying the relationship between language and values, axiolinguistics serves as an important

methodological basis for analyzing the new layers of meaning appearing in internet communication. The article demonstrates how social, cultural, and moral values are expressed through language in Uzbek network discourse (particularly on platforms such as Telegram, Instagram, and TikTok). It also presents scientific observations on the transformation of values in social networks, the formation of new lexical units, and their axio-semantic nature.

Keywords: axiolinguistics, values, social network, virtual communication, internet language, axio-semantics, culture, communication.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются способы выражения ценностей через языковые единицы в социальных сетях, процесс приобретения ими аксиологического содержания, а также формирование новых семантических свойств языка в условиях виртуального общения. Аксиолингвистика, как новое направление, изучающее взаимосвязь языка и ценностей, служит важной методологической основой для анализа новых смысловых слоёв, возникающих в интернет-коммуникации. В статье показаны способы выражения социальных, культурных и нравственных ценностей через язык узбекского сетевого общения (в частности, на платформах Telegram, Instagram и TikTok). Кроме того, приводятся научные наблюдения о трансформации ценностей в социальных сетях, появлении новых лексических единиц и их аксио-семантической природе.

Ключевые слова: аксиолингвистика, ценность, социальная сеть, виртуальное общение, язык интернета, аксиосемантика, культура, коммуникация.

So‘nggi yillarda inson faoliyatining deyarli barcha sohalarida raqamli texnologiyalar chuqur kirib kelmoqda. Xususan, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar - insonlar o‘rtasidagi muloqot, axborot almashinuvi va qadriyatlar tizimini shakllantirishda muhim kommunikativ maydonga aylandi. Bu jarayonda til faqat aloqa vositasi emas, balki madaniy va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni ifodalovchi va uzatuvchi asosiy mexanizm sifatida namoyon bo‘lmoqda. Aksiolingvistika fanining asosiy maqsadi - til orqali qadriyatlarni tahlil qilish, ularning leksik, semantik va pragmatik darajada qanday ifoda topishini o‘rganishdir. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar tili aksiolingvistik tahlil uchun boy material hisoblanadi, chunki bu makonda so‘z, ibora va belgilar o‘zining an‘anaviy ma‘nosidan tashqari yangi qadriyat yuklamasini oladi. Masalan, “like”, “follow”, “trend”, “repost” kabi so‘zlar o‘zbek tarmoq tilida nafaqat texnik tushunchani, balki ijtimoiy maqom, jamiyatda tan olinishi yoki axloqiy qadriyatni ifodalash vositasiga aylangan. Demak, ijtimoiy tarmoq tili qadriyatlarning zamonaviy ko‘rinishini, ya‘ni virtual aksiologiyani shakllantiradi.

Aksiolingvistika (yunoncha axios - “qadriyat”, lingua - “til”) tilshunoslikning nisbatan yangi yo‘nalishlaridan biri bo‘lib, u til orqali qadriyatlarning qanday ifoda topishi, uzatilishi va qabul qilinishini o‘rganadi. Bu yo‘nalish tilni nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki jamiyatning axloqiy, estetik, madaniy va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarini ifodalovchi tizim sifatida talqin qiladi. Aksiologik tilshunoslik ham antropotsentrik xarakterga egaligi bilan alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Borliqdagi narsa-buyum, voqea-hodisalar yolg‘iz inson ongidagina qadriyat sifatida muhimlik kasb etadi [2:526]. Aksiolingvistik tadqiqotlarda til axloqiy-madaniy mazmuni tashuvchi belgilar tizimi sifatida ko‘riladi. Tilning har bir birligi (so‘z, ibora, maqol, mem, emoji va h.k.) ma‘lum bir qadriyatni bildirishi yoki unga qarshi turuvchi antiqadriyatni ifodalashi mumkin. Aksiolingvistika bir necha fanlar bilan uzviy bog‘liq:

Falsafa – qadriyat tushunchasining mohiyatini belgilaydi;

Madaniyatshunoslik – qadriyatlarning tarixiy shakllanishini tushuntiradi; Sotsiologiya - qadriyatlarning jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy rolini tahlil qiladi;

Lingvistika – qadriyatlarning til orqali ifodalanish mexanizmini o‘rganadi.

Bu fanlar integratsiyasi natijasida aksiolingvistika madaniy semantika, diskurs tahlili va sotsiolingvistika bilan ham kesishadi. Masalan, soʻzlarning ijtimoiy konnotatsiyasi (“zamonaviy”, “eskicha”, “milliy”, “liberal”) orqali jamiyatdagi qadriyatlar tizimini aniqlash mumkin. Tilshunos olimlarning fikricha, aksiolingvistika tilning faqat lingvistik emas, balki aksiosemantik (qadriyatli maʼnolarni shakllantiruvchi) xususiyatlarini ham oʻrganadi. Shunday qilib, bu yoʻnalish tilni qadriyatlar olamining oynasi sifatida talqin qiladi. “Qadriyatlar inson hayotining muhim qismlaridan biri boʻlib, ularning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi jamiyat va shaxsiy hayotda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu qadriyatlar inson faoliyatining meʼzonlari va unda amalga oshiriladigan harakatlarni belgilaydi” [1:15]

XXI asrda til taraqqiyotining yangi bosqichi - virtual til makoni vujudga keldi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar (Telegram, Instagram, TikTok, X (Twitter), Facebook) tilning tez oʻzgaruvchi, dinamik shaklini yaratdi. Bu makonda soʻzlar koʻpincha emosional, ironik yoki baholovchi maʼnolarni oladi.

Aksiolingvistik nuqtai nazardan, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda quyidagi qadriyat turlari til orqali faol ifodalanadi:

1. Shaxsiy qadriyatlar. “Men kimman?”, “Men nima uchun bunday yashayman?” kabi savollarga javob sifatida postlar, selfilar, “motivatsion iqtiboslar” paydo boʻladi. Masalan: “Har kuni oʻzingning eng yaxshi versiyang boʻl.” Bu ibora oʻzlikni qadrlash (self-respect) va individualizm qadriyatini ifodalaydi.

2. Ijtimoiy qadriyatlar. Jamiyatda birdamlik, yordam, hamdardlik kabi qadriyatlar ham tarmoq tilida ifodalanadi: “Bir-biringizni asrang”, “Yordam kerak boʻlsa, yozing”, “Duo soʻrayman”. Bu kabi birliklar tarmoq tilida ijtimoiy empatiya va milliy mehr-oqibat qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi.

3. Estetik va madaniy qadriyatlar. Instagram va TikTok tarmoqlarida estetik qadriyatlar - goʻzallik, zamonaviylik, moda, dizayn, ovoz, vizual uygʻunlik orqali ifodalanadi. Tarmoqdagi “trend”, “style”, “aesthetic” kabi soʻzlar yangi estetik qadriyat mezonlarini belgilaydi.

Shunday qilib, ijtimoiy tarmoq tili qadriyatlar tizimining koʻzgusi boʻlib, unda ijobiy va salbiy aksio birliklar bir vaqtning oʻzida mavjud boʻladi. Virtual muloqot - bu real muloqotning raqamli muhitda qayta shakllangan koʻrinishidir. “Virtual aloqa matn, audio va video xabarlardan foydalangan holda kompyuterlar va mobil qurilmalar orqali muloqot qilishni oʻz ichiga oladi. Bunga ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, messenjerlar va raqamli aloqaning boshqa shakllari kiradi” [3]. Unda ishtirokchilar soʻzlashuv, yozishuv, emoji, stiker, gif va memlar orqali oʻz hissiyotlarini, fikrlarini va qadriyatlarini ifoda etadilar. Shu jarayonda qadriyatlar tildagi yangi ifoda vositalari orqali oʻzgaradi, baʼzida esa yangi aksio birliklar paydo boʻladi. Masalan, “❤️” emojiʼsi tarmoq tilida nafaqat muhabbat yoki duo maʼnosini, balki hurmat, qoʻllab-quvvatlash, mehr qadriyatlarini ifodalovchi universal belgiga aylangan. Shuningdek, “🔥” belgisi koʻpincha “zoʻr”, “aʼlo”, “trendda” maʼnolarida ishlatilib, zamonaviylik va muvaffaqiyat qadriyatini bildiradi. Virtual muloqotda tilning emotiv (hissiy) xususiyati kuchayadi. Bunda soʻzning semantik yadrosi emas, balki uning hissiy konnotatsiyasi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Masalan, “goʻzal” soʻzi real hayotda estetik qadriyatni anglatrsa, tarmoqlarda “goʻzal joy”, “goʻzal post”, “goʻzal fikr” kabi shakllarda kengaytirilgan aksiologik maʼnoda qoʻllanadi. Bundan tashqari, virtual makonda “soxta qadriyatlar” ham shakllanmoqda. “Layklar” soni, “koʻruvlar” miqdori yoki “obunachilar” soni koʻpincha shaxsning ijtimoiy qadri sifatida baholanmoqda. Bu holatda qadriyatlar mazmuniy emas, koʻrsatkichli (statistik) shaklga oʻtadi. Shuning uchun zamonaviy aksiolingvistika virtual qadriyatlar va haqiqiy qadriyatlar oʻrtasidagi chegarani aniqlashni muhim ilmiy vazifa

sifatida belgilaydi. Virtual muhitda qadriyatlarining o'zgarishi quyidagi jarayonlar orqali kechadi:

Semantik qisqarish – so'zlarning ma'nosi soddalashadi ("brat", "siss", "top");

Metaforik kengayish – oddiy so'z yangi ijtimoiy ma'no kasb etadi ("trendda bo'lish", "viral post"); Aksiologik inversiya – qadriyat ma'nosining teskari talqini ("kulish uchun jiddiy mavzularni memga aylantirish").

Aksiolingvistik yondashuv ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi tilni faqat kommunikativ vosita sifatida emas, balki qadriyatlarni ifodalovchi, o'zgartiruvchi va shakllantiruvchi ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Virtual makon - bu real jamiyatning lingvistik va aksiosemantik modeli bo'lib, unda milliy, diniy, estetik va ijtimoiy qadriyatlar raqamli ifodasini topadi.

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O'ZBEK TILINING IJTIMOIIY HAYOTDAGI O'RNI VA YOSH AVLOD ONGIDAGI TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilining tarixiy rivojlanishi, uning ijtimoiy hayotdagi rolini tahlil qilish orqali, tilning davlat boshqaruvi, ta'lim, ommaviy axborot vositalari va yoshlar ongidagi ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Metod sifatida kuzatuv, tahlil va taqqoslash usullari qo'llanildi. Natijalardan ma'lum bo'lishicha, til faqat muloqot vositasi emas, balki millatning madaniy va ma'naviy yuzidir. Maqolada yoshlar orasida til madaniyatini shakllantirishga doir taklif va mulohazalar ham bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbek tili, davlat tili, til madaniyati, ta'lim, yoshlar, ijtimoiy hayot, milliy o'zlik, til bayrami.

Har bir millatning milliy o'zligini belgilab beruvchi eng muhim omillardan biri -bu uning ona tilidir. Til nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki xalqning tarixiy xotirasi, madaniyati, an'anasi va hayotiy qarashlarini o'z ichiga olgan boy ma'naviy meros hisoblanadi. O'zbek tili -buyuk o'tmishga ega, ildizlari chuqur tarixga borib taqaladigan tillardan biri bo'lib, 1989 yil 21 oktyabrda "O'zbek tilining davlat tili sifatida" e'tirof etilishi orqali uning maqomi yanada yuksak pog'onaga ko'tarildi. Ushbu maqolada tilning ijtimoiy hayotdagi roli, yoshlar ongidagi o'rni, ta'lim va axborot makonidagi mavqei, shuningdek, uni rivojlantirishga oid amaliy choralar tahlil qilinadi.

Til har qanday jamiyatning madaniy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy hayotida muhim o'rin tutadi. Ayniqsa, davlat tili maqomiga ega bo'lgan til -xalqning boshqaruv, ta'lim, fan va ommaviy axborot tizimlaridagi birdamligini ta'minlovchi asosiy vositadir. Mustaqillik yillarida O'zbekistonda davlat tilini rivojlantirish, uning nufuzi va qo'llanish doirasini kengaytirish bo'yicha tizimli chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirildi.

Bugungi globalashuv va axborot texnologiyalari asrida o'z ona tilini asrash va uni yanada rivojlantirish dolzarb masalaga aylanmoqda. Tillararo raqobat kuchaygan bir sharoitda o'zbek tili o'z mavqeini saqlab qolish, yosh avlod ongi va ijtimoiy ongda barqaror o'rin egallashi uchun yangicha yondashuvlarni, ilmiy asoslangan til siyosatini talab qiladi.

Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tilining bugungi kundagi holati, uni o'rganish va qo'llashdagi muammolar va imkoniyatlar, shuningdek, yoshlarda ona tiliga nisbatan mas'uliyatni shakllantirish yo'llari ilmiy tahlil etiladi.

Ushbu tadqiqotda o'zbek tilining ijtimoiy hayotdagi o'rni, ta'lim tizimidagi mavqei va yoshlar ongidagi ta'sirini o'rganish maqsadida quyidagi ilmiy-amaliy metodlardan foydalanildi:

1. Kuzatuv usuli: O'zbek tilining jamiyatdagi qo'llanilish holatlarini tahlil qilishda birinchi navbatda tabiiy va maqsadli kuzatuv olib borildi. Davlat idoralari, ta'lim muassasalari va ommaviy axborot vositalarida tildan foydalanish ko'lami kuzatildi. Maktablarda o'tkazilgan til bayrami tadbirlari, kitobxonlik kechalari va tanlovlar orqali yoshlar ongida tilga bo'lgan munosabatni kuzatish imkoni paydo bo'ldi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda (Telegram, Instagram, YouTube) o'zbek tilidagi kontentlarning tarqalishi va foydalanuvchilar munosabati kuzatildi.

2. Tahlil va kontent tahlili: O'rganilayotgan mavzu doirasidagi turli materiallar, qonun hujjatlari, dunyoqarashni shakllantiruvchi ommaviy nutqlar, ta'lim dasturlari va mediamatnlar tahlil qilindi: "Davlat tili haqida"gi qonun, Prezident farmonlari va konsepsiya hujjatlari o'rganildi. Ta'lim muassasalaridagi "O'zbek tili" fanidan darsliklar va o'quv qo'llanmalar kontent tahliliga tortilib, ulardagi lingvistik yundalishlar, tarbiyaviy jihatlar va til madaniyati elementlari o'rganildi.

Blogerlar va ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali tarqalgan tildagi nutq (mulohazalar, videolar) mazmun va uslub jihatidan tahlil qilindi.

3. So'rovnoma va intervyular (fokus guruh shaklida): Tadqiqotning amaliy qismida o'quvchi va talabalar o'rtasida so'rovnoma o'tkazildi. Savollar asosan tilga munosabat, uning foydalanish doirasi va kelajagi haqidagi fikrlarga qaratildi. 50 nafar 10–11-sinf o'quvchilari va 30 nafar talabalar ishtirokida so'rovnoma o'tkazildi. Quyidagi savollarga javob olindi:

O'zbek tilida fikr yuritish darajasi qanday?

Sizningcha, til qanday sohalarda keng qo'llanilmoqda?

Televideniye va internetda o'zbek tili kontentiga bo'lgan munosabatingiz?

O'zbek tili kelajagi haqida fikringiz?

Shuningdek, ikki nafar ona tili o'qituvchisi va bir tilshunos olim bilan qo'shimcha intervyular tashkil etildi.

4. Qiyosiy tahlil usuli: O'zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi qo'llanilish darajasi boshqa davlatlar -xususan, Qozog'iston, Qirg'iziston, Turkiya kabi mamlakatlarda davlat tilining rivojlanishi bilan taqqoslandi. Bu qiyosiy yondashuv o'zbek tilining istiqbolini baholashga yordam berdi.

5. Ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish: Mavzuga oid ilmiy va metodik adabiyotlar -tilshunoslik, ijtimoiy lingvistika, sosiologiya, ta'lim metodikasiga oid risolalar o'rganildi. Xususan, tilning ijtimoiy funksiyalari, yoshlarda milliy o'zlikni shakllantirishdagi roli bo'yicha ilmiy qarashlar tahlil etildi.

Yuqoridagi natijalar asosida tilning ijtimoiy hayotdagi mavqeini yanada mustahkamlash uchun quyidagi masalalar muhokama qilindi: Til siyosatini takomillashtirish: davlat hujjatlari va ta'lim materiallarining barcha sohalarda to'liq o'zbek tilida yuritilishini ta'minlash muhim. Til madaniyatini oshirish: maktab va oliygohlarda tilga oid fanlarni faqat grammatika emas, balki jonli muloqot, ijodiy yozish, nutq madaniyati asosida o'qitish zarur. Media savodxonligi va til: bloggerlar, jurnalistlar va kontent yaratuvchilar uchun til madaniyati bo'yicha o'quv kurslari joriy etish taklif etiladi.

Yoshlar uchun motivatsiya yaratish: tilda yaxshi gapiradigan, toza yozadigan yoshlarga rag‘bat sifatida tanlovlar, stipendiyalar, media imkoniyatlar berish. Shevaviy nutq muammosi: har bir hududning o‘ziga xosligi inobatga olingan holda, adabiy til qoidalariga e‘tiborni kuchaytirish.

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INTERACTIVE METHODS OF WORKING WITH PROVERBS IN ENGLISH LESSONS AT A LANGUAGE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the specifics of using interactive methods in teaching English proverbs at a language university. Proverbs, being an important part of the cultural heritage of the people, have significant didactic potential. They not only contribute to enriching the vocabulary of students, but also develop their intercultural competence, form critical thinking and the ability to interpret semantic nuances. The author emphasizes that the use of interactive methods such as group work, quests, project assignments, role-playing games and digital tools makes the learning process more exciting and effective. The article reveals specific forms and techniques of working with proverbs in English classes, as well as provides examples of methodological exercises.

Keywords: interactive methods, English proverbs, language university, intercultural communication, critical thinking, creative learning, group work, project activities, digital tools, communicative competence.

Introduction: Modern methods of teaching foreign languages are aimed not only at developing language skills, but also at developing students' ability to understand the culture, values and worldview of native speakers. Proverbs are one of the most striking carriers of the national picture of the world, as they reflect the centuries-old experience of the people, their moral attitudes and peculiarities of thinking. In this regard, working with proverbs in English lessons is becoming particularly important, especially in language universities, where future specialists are preparing for professional activity in a multilingual and multicultural environment.

However, traditional teaching methods (reading, translation, memorization) often turn out to be insufficiently effective, since they do not arouse students' active cognitive interest. That is why the introduction of interactive methods is becoming an urgent task for teachers who strive to make the learning process lively, creative and motivating.

2. Theoretical foundations of the use of proverbs in education: Proverbs have a high didactic value. They are concise, expressive, easy to remember, and often contain stable grammatical and lexical constructions that can be used to teach various aspects of the language. Firstly, proverbs allow students to expand their vocabulary by introducing them into the context of stable expressions and idiomatic constructions. Secondly, they contribute to the formation of socio-cultural competence, as they familiarize students with the norms of behavior, ethical attitudes and cultural realities of the country of the target language.

Thirdly, proverbs develop critical thinking, as they encourage students to analyze, compare and interpret the meaning of expressions, finding analogies in their native culture. In addition, working with proverbs contributes to the development of communicative competence, because the discussion of their meaning, context and usage takes place in the process of live communication and exchange of opinions.

3. Interactive methods of working with proverbs: Interactive methods involve the active participation of students in the learning process, where everyone becomes not a passive listener, but a participant in a joint creative search.

1. Discussions and brainstorming. The teacher suggests several proverbs on a specific topic (for example, "friendship", "work", "time") and organizes a discussion. Students explain how they understand the meaning of statements, cite similar proverbs from their native language,

and discuss differences in cultural beliefs. This type of work contributes to the development of analytical thinking and oral speech.

2. Role-playing games. Proverbs can be used as replicas of characters in mini-skits. For example, when studying the proverb “Actions speak louder than words”, one group of students can prepare a scene illustrating the meaning of this statement, and the other can determine what kind of morality it contains.

3. Quests and game tasks. Students receive assignments related to the search for "hidden" proverbs in texts, songs, films or on online platforms. Such exercises arouse great interest and create conditions for informal learning of the material.

4. Project activities. Projects can be aimed at researching English proverbs on topics ("Wisdom and Foolishness", "Love and Friendship", "Work and Success") or comparing them with Uzbek equivalents. The result of the project can be a presentation, a mini-video or a poster.

5. Digital technologies. Using online platforms (Kahoot, Padlet, Quizlet, Mentimeter) allows you to create interactive quizzes, tests and flash cards. Digital forms of work make learning flexible, modern and accessible even in a remote format.

4. Methodological recommendations:

1. Selection of the material. Proverbs should be chosen thematically, in accordance with the lexical material of the textbook or the current topic.

2. Contextual learning. Each proverb should be used in context: in a text, dialogue, or situation, and not in isolation.

3. Comparative analysis. It is important to compare English proverbs with their counterparts in the students' native language, discussing differences in mentality and perception of the world.

4. Discussion and reflection. After completing the assignments, students are invited to discuss which proverbs they liked, which ones they consider relevant today, and which ones are outdated. This stimulates a personal attitude towards language.

5. Integration with other activities. Proverbs can be used in teaching writing (essays, letters), reading (texts in which proverbs occur), as well as in developing listening skills (songs, podcasts).

5. Practical implementation and results: Practice shows that the use of interactive methods of working with proverbs increases students' motivation to learn a language, activates their speech activity and promotes better memorization of the material.

For example, during a lesson on “Work and Success”, students are introduced to proverbs:

“No pain, no gain.”

“Hard work pays off.”

“Rome wasn't built in a day.”

After discussing the meaning and context, the teacher organizes a mini-debate on the topic of diligence, where students use the learned proverbs in speech. This form of work helps to integrate lexical and communication skills.

Students note that with the help of interactive tasks, they begin to perceive proverbs not as formal linguistic units, but as living elements of culture capable of expressing deep thoughts in simple words.

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PHONETIC CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO UZBEK- SPEAKING LEARNERS

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Abstract. English is widely used as a communication tool in the world today. Due to this, the requirements for effective teaching of English in Uzbekistan are increasing. The phonetic systems of English and Uzbek languages have their own significant differences, which makes their use difficult for Uzbek speakers. Three articles analyze the most common pronunciation problems of Uzbek students, the phonetic foundations of the document, and practical methods for overcoming them. The main problems are related to the wider vowel system of the English language, consonant clusters, stress and intonation features, and situations with unfamiliar sounds. The article proposes a systematic approach to overcome these processes, combining the development of phonetics, listening comprehension, articulatory training, and communicative practices.

Key words: Vowel system, diphthong, consonant clusters, stress and intonation, voicing contrast, monotone intonation, phonetic awareness, transcription, minimal pair drills, articulatory training, technology-enhanced learning.

English is the world's leading language of science, technology, business, and education. In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to learning English at the state level. Although more emphasis is placed on grammar and vocabulary development, pronunciation is often considered a secondary skill. In fact, clear and correct pronunciation is one of the most important factors in understandable speech and confident communication for Uzbek students. The phonetic systems of English and Uzbek differ significantly in terms of the number of vowels, the structure of consonants, and prosodic features. While Uzbek has a relatively stable and simple sound system, English is characterized by a wider vowel inventory, complex syllable structure, and variable stress. These differences cause persistent pronunciation problems for Uzbek students. This article aims to identify these problems and offer methodological recommendations that will help overcome them. Uzbek generally has six main vowels, which are stable in quality and length. English has twelve pure vowels and several diphthongs. For example, it is difficult for Uzbek learners to distinguish between the short /ɪ/ (bit) and the long /i:/ (beat) sounds, since in Uzbek there is almost no contrast based on vowel length. Also, diphthongs such as /aɪ/ (time), /eɪ/ (say) require complex language movements that do not exist in Uzbek.

Consonant clusters. In Uzbek, it is rare for several consonants to appear in succession at the beginning or end of a syllable. In English, clusters such as /str-/ (street), /spl-/ (splash) are widespread. Learners often simplify them: for example, saying *esport* instead of *sport* or dropping the sounds.

Stress and intonation. In Uzbek, stress is almost constant and the tone of speech is more even. In English, stress is variable, and intonation is actively used to express meaning, contrast, or emotion. Because of this difference, Uzbek learners of English may speak in a monotonous manner or misplace stress.

Unfamiliar consonants. English contains sounds that are not found in Uzbek, such as the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ (think, this). Learners often replace them with /t/, /s/, or /z/ (think instead of tink). The labiodental sound /v/ can also be confused with /w/.

Common Pronunciation Problems. The above phonetic differences create the following problems in the speech of Uzbek students:

Substitution of unfamiliar sounds – using /t/ or /s/ instead of /θ/.

Failure to distinguish minimal pairs – such as ship/sheep, bit/beat.

Reduction of consonant clusters – pronouncing col instead of cold.

Improper stress – the habit of stressing the last syllable.

Monotonous intonation – speech sounds dull or incomprehensible due to a flat tone.

Teaching strategies. To overcome these problems, targeted and systematic pronunciation training is necessary. The following approaches are effective:

Phonetic awareness and transcription. Working with the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) makes it easier for students to see and feel the differences between sounds.

Minimal pair exercises. The ability to distinguish sounds is developed by listening to and saying sounds such as ship/sheep, pen/pan.

Articulation training. Using a diagram, video, or mirror to show mouth, tongue, and lip positions, such as placing the tongue between the teeth for the sound /θ/.

Step-by-step practice of consonant clusters. First, learn simple, then complex clusters.

Stress and intonation exercises. Master the rhythm and tone of English through dialogues, songs, and short speeches.

Technological tools. Pronunciation checking apps, the ability to write and listen to enhance self-control.

Integrating these techniques into the communicative part of the lesson, rather than as stand-alone exercises, will sustainably develop students' pronunciation.

The phonetic difficulties for Uzbek speakers in learning English are rooted in several key differences: the limited number of vowel sounds, the complexity of consonant clusters, the variability of stress and intonation, and the presence of unfamiliar sounds. However, these challenges can be effectively overcome through a combination of systematic phonetic preparation, listening comprehension exercises, articulation training, and technological tools. Putting pronunciation at the center of the teaching process will help Uzbek learners speak English clearly, fluently, and confidently, and will enhance their academic and professional opportunities.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH FOR GLOBAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. This article extensively discusses the importance of the English language in globalization processes, its role as a means of international communication, and its impact on various aspects of social life. The role of the English language in the fields of education, diplomacy, technology, economics, and cultural exchange is analyzed in depth. The role of language as a factor influencing personal development and professional success is also shown. The article is written on the basis of modern scientific sources and regulatory documents.

Keywords: English language, global communication, international cooperation, education, technology, economics, cultural exchange, language policy, tourism.

In the current era of rapid globalization, people living in different parts of the world are increasingly able to communicate with each other quickly and effectively. The need for a common language is growing to ensure mutual understanding between societies of different cultures, nationalities, and languages. In this regard, English has become the most important tool of international communication. English is now taught and used as a second language on almost all continents of the world. It plays a leading role in diplomatic communication, international trade, scientific research, technological innovation, cultural exchange, and education. Knowledge of English is considered an important condition for active participation in global processes, mastering modern knowledge and technologies, and achieving personal and professional success. English has become the official working language of many international organizations. For example, meetings, negotiations, and documents are conducted in English at the UN, UNESCO, the World Health Organization, and many other institutions. This language facilitates understanding between representatives of different countries, simplifies diplomatic processes, and strengthens cooperation. In addition, international summits, global forums, and conferences are also organized mainly in English.

Therefore, for those working in the diplomatic field, a deep knowledge of this language has become a necessary competency. Today, education is conducted in English at the most prestigious higher education institutions-Oxford, Cambridge, Harvard, MIT, and others. More than 80% of internationally ranked scientific journals are published in English. Knowledge of the language allows people to establish direct contact with the scientific community, master best practices, and take their research to the global scientific arena. English is also required to participate in many grants, exchange programs, and international projects. Today, English is not only a means of international communication but also an important key to science, technology, and intercultural exchange. Scientific literature, books, textbooks, and magazines about modern technologies created in different parts of the world are mainly written in English. Therefore, it holds particular importance as the main language that provides free access to modern information. English also plays a vital role in travel and tourism. Since tourism is international in nature, a single understandable language is necessary in relations between different countries. Many travel agencies, airlines, hotels, and international companies offer their services primarily in English. People traveling to foreign countries need a common language to communicate effectively with the local population, and English is the most widely used language for this purpose.

Therefore, a thorough study of English not only provides direct access to scientific information but also opens wide doors for successful work in the modern world, participation in global intercultural dialogue, and professional development. English also occupies a leading position in the field of information technology. The main terminology of

programming languages, technical documentation, online courses, scientific research, and most modern innovative solutions are written in English. The fact that more than half of the content on the Internet is created in English also demonstrates its global importance. Knowledge of the language allows people to quickly master modern technologies and actively participate in the global digital space. In the global economy, English is considered a universal business language. International companies, financial institutions, and trade organizations use it in their daily operations. In many countries, knowledge of English is a key requirement for highly qualified jobs. Specialists with language skills expand international cooperation, can enter foreign markets, and have greater opportunities for professional growth. Moreover, knowing English broadens personal horizons, helps accept new ideas, and forms the basis for open communication in multicultural societies. The international prestige and importance of English have increased immeasurably in the process of globalization. It now serves as the main tool in international business relations, science and technology, diplomatic meetings, and global information exchange. The widespread use of English facilitates mutual understanding between different peoples and expands opportunities for economic and cultural cooperation. Therefore, English is recognized as a “common language” worldwide [4; 300-b].

However, this process is not one-sided. The dominance of English also creates certain negative consequences. First, it can exacerbate linguistic inequality—those who speak English fluently often gain advantages, while those with insufficient language proficiency are excluded from global communication. Moreover, cultural diversity and the significance of national languages may decline, potentially weakening cultural identity. For non-native speakers, language barriers, translation issues, and unequal opportunities can hinder full participation in the international arena. Solving these problems requires a multi-stage and systematic approach. Education systems should not only focus on in-depth English teaching but also on developing multilingual competence in students. This ensures success in the global arena while preserving national languages and cultures. It is also essential to expand the use of multiple languages in international organizations and forums. This helps amplify diverse voices, respect different viewpoints, and create a dialogue-based environment rooted in equality. Developing effective English teaching methods, improving translation technologies, and forming fair language policies are crucial steps on this path. Thus, by maintaining the positive aspects of English as a global means of communication while addressing its negative effects, it is possible to create a more inclusive and fairer linguistic environment. The ultimate goal is to make English a bridge connecting different peoples—not a barrier dividing them. In short, English has become the most significant tool for global communication today. It plays a crucial role not only in international diplomacy, education, and technology but also in economics and culture. Mastery of the language allows individuals to communicate freely on the international stage, demonstrate their knowledge and potential, and become active participants in global processes. Therefore, learning English should be one of the top priorities not only in educational policy but also in personal development strategies.

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YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA TIL TA’LIMIDA YUTUQLAR VA MUAMMOLAR

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Xorijiy til va adabiyot yo‘nalishi 1-bosqich talabasi

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Yangi O‘zbekiston davrida til siyosati va ta’lim tizimidagi islohotlar tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, davlat tilining maqomini mustahkamlash, xorijiy tillarni o‘qitish tizimini modernizatsiya qilish, ta’lim metodikalarini zamonaviylashtirish borasidagi yutuqlar yoritiladi. Shu bilan birga, til ta’limidagi mavjud muammolar, ularning sabablari va bartaraf etish yo‘llari ham atroflicha tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada xalqaro tajriba va amaliyotlarga asoslangan holda taklif va tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Yangi O‘zbekiston, til siyosati, til ta’limi, davlat tili, xorijiy tillar, ta’lim, ta’lim islohotlari, metodika.

Abstract: This article analyzes language policy and educational reforms in the era of New Uzbekistan. In particular, it highlights achievements in strengthening the status of the state language, modernizing the system of foreign language teaching, and updating teaching methodologies. At the same time, the article provides a comprehensive analysis of existing challenges in language education, their causes, and possible solutions. Based on international experience and best practices, the paper also offers several recommendations and proposals for further improvement.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, language policy, language education, state language, foreign languages, education, educational reforms, methodology.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются языковая политика и реформы в системе образования в эпоху Нового Узбекистана. В частности, освещаются достижения в укреплении статуса государственного языка, модернизации системы преподавания иностранных языков и обновлении методик обучения. Одновременно подробно рассматриваются существующие проблемы в языковом образовании, их причины и пути устранения. На основе международного опыта и практики в статье представлены предложения и рекомендации по дальнейшему совершенствованию данной сферы.

Ключевые слова: Новый Узбекистан, языковая политика, языковое образование, государственный язык, иностранные языки, образование, образовательные реформы, методика

Til-bu millatning ruhi, madaniyati, tafakkuri va tarixining timsolidir. Har bir davlatning mustaqilligi va suvereniteti, eng avvalo, o‘z davlat tilining huquqiy maqomi, nufuzi va hayotdagi amaliy qo‘llanilishi darajasi bilan belgilanadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, mustaqillik yillarida, ayniqsa, Yangi O‘zbekiston davrida til siyosati va ta’limi borasida tub o‘zgarishlar amalga oshirilmogda. Davlat tilining nufuzi yanada keng qamrovga olinmogda, chet tillarini o‘qitish tizimi tubdan isloh qilinmogda, ko‘p tilli ta’lim modeliga o‘tish tajribalari sinovdan o‘tkazilmogda. Mustaqillik yillarida, ayniqsa, so‘nggi yillarda Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyotining muhim yo‘nalishlaridan biri sifatida ta’lim tizimini isloh qilish,

jumladan, til ta'limini zamon talablari asosida takomillashtirish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Til –nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki milliy o'zlik, madaniyat va taraqqiyot ko'zgusi hisoblanadi. Shu bois, davlat tilining mavqeini mustahkamlash, xorijiy tillarni o'rganishni rag'batlantirish hamda ko'p tillilik madaniyatini shakllantirish borasida keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida olib borilayotgan til siyosati va ta'lim tizimidagi yangiliklar muayyan natijalarni bergan bo'lsa-da, bu yo'nalishda hali o'z yechimini kutayotgan muammolar ham mavjud. Ushbu maqolada til ta'limi sohasida erishilgan yutuqlar, amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar va uchrayotgan dolzarb muammolar tahlil qilinadi.

2019-yil 21-oktabrda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi nufuzini oshirish va uni rivojlantirish bo'yicha" farmoni e'lon qilindi. Bu farmon asosida davlat tilining huquqiy asoslarini mustahkamlash, davlat idoralarida to'liq qo'llanilishini ta'minlash, hujjat yuritishni o'zbek tilida olib borish kabi muhim vazifalar belgilanadi. Yangi O'zbekistonda chet tillar, ayniqsa, ingliz tilini o'rgatishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalaridan tortib oliy o'quv yurtlarigacha chet tilini o'qitish bo'yicha yangicha yondashuvlar joriy etildi. Xususan, 2021-yilda "Chet tillarni o'rganishni ommalashtirish" bo'yicha Prezident qarori qabul qilindi. Xalqaro sertifikatlariga ega bo'lgan ingliz tili o'qituvchilariga qo'shimcha ustama va imtiyozlar berilmoqda. Shu bilan birgalikda, zamonaviy darsliklar, mobil ilovalar, onlayn platformalar keng joriy etilmoqda. Shuningdek, ba'zi maktablarda hamda litseylarda o'zbek, rus, ingliz tillarida dars mashg'ulotlari olib boriladigan sinflar tashkil etildi. Bu islohotlar nafaqat xorijiy tillarni o'rganishga, balki bolalarning muloqot madaniyati va fikrlash salohiyatini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy texnologiyalar orqali til o'rganish imkoniyatlari kengaymoqda. Hozirgi kunda, foydalanuvchilar tomonidan so'ralayotgan til o'rganish platformalari qulayligi hamda samaradorligi bilan boshqa sayt va ilovalardan farqli o'laroq keng qamrovda foydalanilmoqda. Misol tariqasida "Bilimdon" platformasi. Ushbu platforma orqali o'rganuvchi nafaqat grammatikani, balki tushunish, gapirish, yozish va tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalarini ham rivojlantiradi. Platforma har qanday vaqtda, istalgan joyda til o'rganish imkonini beradi. Bu ayniqsa, band odamlar uchun juda foydalidir. Shu bilan birgalikda, platforma orqali boshqa o'rganuvchilar bilan fikr almashish, mashqlarni birgalikda bajarish va til muhitida bo'lish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, bu va bu kabi platformalar mustaqil hamda tizimli o'rganish imkoniyatining mavjudligi, o'quvchilarning til bilish darajasini bosqichma-bosqich shakllantirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ushbu turdagi platformalarning imkoniyatlari ta'lim jarayoning innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida tashkil etilishiga xizmat qiladi va motivatsion jihatdan rag'batlantiruvchi holatga keltiradi. Olib borilayotgan islohotlardan yana biri shundaki, 2025-yildan boshlab, oliy ma'lumotli va o'z mutaxassislik fanlaridan davlat hamda xalqaro sertifikatlariga ega bo'lgan o'qituvchilarga belgilangan ish stavkasiga qo'shimcha ravishda 50 foiz miqdorda ustama to'lanishi nazarda tutilgan. Shu tariqa, xalqaro sertifikatlariga ega bo'lgan o'qituvchilarga ustama to'lanishi ularning mehnatini rag'batlantirishga va ta'lim sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Hududlar bo'yicha til o'qituvchilar malakasi bo'yicha katta tafovut mavjud. O'zbekiston Respublikasida ham umumiy o'rta ta'lim sifatini oshirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Biroq, respublikaning chekka va olis hududlarida o'qituvchilar yetishmovchiligi hali-hanuz dolzarb muammo bo'lib qolmoqda. Bu holat ta'lim sifati, o'quvchilarning bilim darajasi va teng imkoniyatlar talabiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Chekka hududlarda o'qituvchilar tanqisligini bartaraf etish ta'lim tizimining barqaror rivojlanishi uchun muhim omildir. Oliy ta'lim muassasalari bilan hamkorlikda har bir chekka hudud uchun mahalliy kadrlar zaxirasini yaratish, til sohasida esa har bir tuman uchun alohida

“native speakerlar va leaderlar”ni maqsadli yo‘naltirish. Aynan chekka hududda ishlayotgan o‘qituvchilarning muvaffaqiyatli tajribalarini ommaviy axborot vositalarida targ‘ib etish. “Eng faol chekka hudud o‘qituvchisi” kabi tanlovlar tashkil etish va g‘oliblarni ham moddiy ham ma‘naviy rag‘batlantirish ishlarini amalga oshirish orqali yoshlar orasida pedagog kasbiga nisbatan ijobiy tassavur yaratishga xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga, mazkur strategiyalarni amaliyotda joriy etish orqali davlat boshqaruvi, mahalliy hokimiyatlar, oliy ta‘lim muassasalari o‘rtasida o‘zaro hamkorlik qilinishi bilan bir qatorda rivojlanishning yangi pog‘onasini zabt etishda ham talaygina ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shunday qilib, chekka hududlarda o‘qituvchilar tanqisligi muammosi nafaqat pedagogik kadrlar siyosatini qayta ko‘rib chiqishni, balki ta‘lim tizimining hududiy adolat tamoyiliga asoslangan holda isloh etilishini taqozo etadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, o‘quvchilarda til o‘rganishga nisbatan ichki qiziqish past, uni faqat imtihon topshirish yoki majburiyat sifatida qabul qilish holatlari ko‘p uchraydi. Bu kabi muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun o‘quv dasturlarida tilni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo‘llashga asoslangan topshiriqlarni ko‘paytirish. Til o‘rganishning foydasi haqida doimiy targ‘ibot va rag‘batlantirish mexanizmlarini yaratish (grantlar, tanlovlar, chet elda o‘qish imkoniyatlari). Shu bilan birgalikda, o‘quvchilarning individual qiziqishlariga mos mavzular asosida darslar tashkil etish. Bu kabi tabiiy til muhitining yetishmasligi, o‘quvchilar o‘rganilayotgan tilni hayotda amaliy qo‘llash imkoniyatiga ega emas. Amalda targ‘ib etish uchun til klub va suhbat guruhlarini tashkil etish. Onlayn muloqot platformalari (pen-pal loyihalari, til almashinuvi) kabi ilovalardan foydalanish o‘quvchining fanga yanada chuqurroq intilishiga sabab bo‘ladi. Shu va shu kabi muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo‘nalishlari, pedagogik jamoalarning malaka oshirishi, texnologik innovatsiyalarni joriy etishlari markaziy o‘rinni egallaydi. Til o‘rganish-bu faqat bilim emas, balki madaniyatlararo muloqot vositasi ekanini anglash, o‘rgatish jarayonini yanada sifatli va maqsadli tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi.

Til-bu jamiyatni birlashtiruvchi vosita, uni asrash va rivojlantirish har bir fuqaroning burchidir. Shu bois, til ta‘limiga jiddiy va tizimli yondashuv, doimiy kuzatuv va pedagogik innovatsiyalar zarur. Til ta‘limini yanada sifatli, ommabop va adolatli qilish orqali biz nafaqat o‘z milliy qadriyatlarimizni asraymiz, balki global raqobatga bardosh bera oladigan yangi avlodni tarbiyalaymiz.

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2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi 2022-2026 yillarda yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyoti strategiyasi to‘g‘risidagi PF-60-son Farmoni.
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PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WRITTEN AND ORAL SPEECH

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Annotation: In this article, the major challenges learners face in developing writing and speaking skills within the field of linguistics are discussed. The research aims to identify existing obstacles and propose pedagogical solutions to overcome them in the educational system. The study is based on literature analysis, questionnaires, and classroom observations. Findings show that difficulties in writing mainly stem from the inconsistent application of grammatical rules, poor organization of ideas, and plagiarism, whereas speaking problems are related to mispronunciation, hesitation, and insufficient vocabulary. Moreover, teachers' overemphasis on theoretical grammar and lack of communicative practice hinder learners' fluency. The paper concludes that enhancing creativity in writing, ensuring logical coherence, and improving pronunciation and lexical competence are key solutions for strengthening linguistic education.

Key words: modern education, challenges, solutions, innovation, methodology, effectiveness.

Introduction: In the context of globalization, learning foreign languages has become one of the essential factors determining individual competitiveness and success. Mastering writing and speaking skills is fundamental to effective communication, creative expression, and intercultural understanding. However, in many educational contexts, learners face persistent challenges in applying grammatical rules accurately in writing and achieving fluency in speaking (Harmer, 2004). These issues are partly due to traditional teaching practices that prioritize theoretical knowledge over practical usage.

In writing, students often lack experience in developing original ideas, structuring coherent texts, and maintaining grammatical accuracy (Ur, 1996). In speaking, limited practice in pronunciation and intonation leads to hesitation and low confidence (Nation, 2009). This article explores these challenges and provides possible solutions to enhance written and spoken language proficiency among linguistics students.

Research Methodology: The study employed a mixed-method approach combining literature analysis, questionnaires, and classroom observations.

Writing Problems: Learners' main difficulties in writing include grammatical inaccuracy, weak logical organization, and restricted vocabulary. Common errors involve misuse of tenses, prepositions, and articles, as noted by Brown (2007), which prevent writing from reaching academic standards. Plagiarism also remains a serious issue, as students tend to copy from online resources instead of producing original content.

Speaking Problems: The most frequently observed difficulties in speaking are incorrect pronunciation, hesitation, and insufficient vocabulary. According to Nation (2009), pronunciation issues - such as the "th" sound in English - are common among non-native speakers. Learners also struggle with fluency due to psychological barriers like anxiety or fear of making mistakes (Nunan, 2003).

Solutions: Modern communicative approaches and learner-centered techniques are found to be effective in addressing these issues. Role plays, debates, peer reviews, and creative writing tasks allow students to express themselves freely while applying linguistic knowledge practically (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). An individual approach that considers students' linguistic backgrounds and motivation is essential for sustainable progress.

Literature analysis: A review of both local and international research highlighted the importance of integrating communicative and cognitive methods in language teaching. Brown's *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching* (2007) provided insight into the psychological foundations of skill development. Harmer's *How to Teach Writing* (2004) emphasized task-based writing instruction, while Ur (1996) and Nation (2009) focused on integrating listening and speaking through communicative practice. To gather empirical data,

a questionnaire was conducted among 150 students and 25 teachers. Results indicated that 70% of students found grammar rules difficult to apply in real contexts, and 60% of teachers cited pronunciation as the main barrier to fluency. Observation of traditional and communicative classrooms showed that students engaged in debates and peer discussions improved faster in both fluency and confidence. Peer review in writing assignments enhanced grammatical accuracy and independent thinking (Edge, 1993).

Analysis and Results The research revealed three main areas requiring attention:

1. Grammatical and lexical difficulties. Students frequently make grammatical errors and repeat limited vocabulary, which reduces text quality and speech coherence (Ellis, 2008). These issues are strongly influenced by native language interference.

2. Lack of creativity and independence. Many learners rely on memorized patterns rather than producing original ideas. Interactive techniques such as debates, collaborative writing, and brainstorming activities proved effective in fostering creativity.

3. Insufficient practice and exposure. Observations showed that the limited use of authentic materials-videos, podcasts, and online platforms - restricted pronunciation and fluency development. Integrating multimedia tools improved natural speech and confidence in real-life communication.

Overall, findings highlight the need to balance grammatical accuracy with fluency and to create communicative environments that promote creativity and motivation.

Discussion: The challenges in developing written and spoken communication are rooted not only in students' weaknesses but also in teaching methods. Many teachers still emphasize grammar theoretically, neglecting communicative competence (Crystal, 2010). Psychological factors, such as fear of errors, further hinder speaking performance. In writing, insufficient feedback and the lack of task-based activities limit learners' ability to think critically (Ur, 1996).

Interactive and communicative approaches supported by modern technology help address these issues. Providing a supportive classroom atmosphere, encouraging risk-taking, and promoting student collaboration increase participation and motivation (Nunan, 2003). The integration of creativity and communicative competence in both writing and speaking ensures a more holistic language learning experience.

In conclusion, the development of written and spoken communication skills in linguistics remains a complex process. Common obstacles include grammatical inaccuracy, limited vocabulary, poor pronunciation, and lack of creative independence. The findings suggest that focusing solely on grammar instruction without practical engagement leads to low communicative competence.

To overcome these challenges, teachers should apply innovative and communicative methodologies, integrate technology, and promote learner-centered instruction. Interactive tasks such as debates, role plays, and peer reviews enhance both writing and speaking skills. Ultimately, the balance between accuracy and fluency, combined with continuous teacher development, can ensure greater effectiveness in modern linguistic education.

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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND MODERN TRENDS: BLENDED LEARNING AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. The digitalization era has transformed the educational system with ever-increasing innovative technologies as a result of which in more amenable learning environments there is a constant flow of new teaching methodologies. The article examines recent research on digital innovations and modern trends in higher education, focusing on blended learning as a core strategy bridging traditional pedagogy and technological advancement. Based on studies by Gashimov and Pestova (2021), Ivanenko et al. (2021), Yang et al. (2024), Danilov et al. (2021), and Bazeliuk (2022), the article explores both opportunities and drawbacks of practical use of blended learning format, which aims to create inclusive and high-quality learning experience for all learners.

Key words: blended learning, digitalization, sustainable education, inclusivity, traditional pedagogy.

The rapid digitalization of the latest decades has affected many areas of society, including education. Within the system every aspect of educational process has been reshaped starting from the general format and ending with the role of a teacher. However, this boost of technological advancement – online platforms, VR teaching and artificial intelligence – raises concerns in proper adaptation of new tools in accordance with the existing values and standards of education. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated these changes even more, literally forcing institutions to put online and blended learning into practice. According to Gashimov and Pestova (2021) argue that digitalization in educational sphere is not just a trend but a real necessity. As demand creates supply, blended learning emerged as a promising solution that combines conservative and innovative instruction.

As a matter of fact, innovation in the context of higher education is multifaceted, ranging from advanced learning management systems to the introduction of adaptive and personalized learning tools. Ivanenko et al. (2021) highlighted that digital tools such as massive open online courses (also known as MOOCs), and virtual learning environments are absolutely essential for modern institutions. In online settings with practically no barriers, doors to many learning opportunities are open for learners of different cultural and geographical backgrounds.

Yang et al. (2024) underline specific innovations such as gamification techniques – where elements of play are incorporated into lessons – improve motivation and persistence. Moreover, artificial intelligence has also become beneficial in language learning, providing much necessary feedback, personalized recommendations, supporting individual student learning. What is more, immersive technologies such as augmented and virtual reality brings abstract concepts to life. In fact, student studying medicine can virtually practice surgical

procedures, an engineering student can simulate building structures, while a history student can literally walk through a reconstructed ancient city. These innovations illustrate how digitalization is expanding the possibilities of education beyond the classroom.

In fact, blended learning has become one of the most influential models used in educational process. It is a mix of face-to-face authentic interaction and the flexibility of online instruction. Danilov et al. (2021) underlines that blended learning might act as not just temporary solution but a sustainable model which is ideal for modern realities of our society. This approach provides students with opportunity to engage either with offline seminars and lectures or online discussions, prerecorded lectures and digital assignments. Utilizing both modes creates this environment of continuous learning where accessibility is ever present.

Research by Yang et al. (2024) proves that blended learning increases satisfaction as well as leads to greater outcomes in academic performance. Once carefully designed, online components allow students to study content at their own pace, while revisiting difficult concepts if needed. Meanwhile, in-person sessions help to maintain the human connection that is often missing in fully online courses. This is certainly helpful to develop soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and critical thinking necessary for modern world.

Despite numerous advantages of digital transformation, we still have significant challenges at hands. Bazeliuk (2022) claims that the greatest barrier is perhaps unequal access to digital infrastructure. Many institutions, especially in developing countries, lack resources to provide reliable internet connection, modern devices and advanced platforms to maintain the quality of education. This evidently opposes the concept of inclusivity in education.

Teacher readiness is another critical challenge. Ivanenko et al. (2021) rightfully refers to the fact that many educators were unprepared for the sudden shift to online teaching during the pandemic. Truly, effective digital teaching comes from not only technical skills but also properly adapted new pedagogical strategies. A typical lecture designed for a classroom does not equal to an engaging online lesson. Thus, teachers must learn how to use digital tools creatively so that fostering interaction and meaningful learning is possible.

Resistance to change is also a factor as traditional education has strong roots in face-to-face communication. There are still some educators and students as well who are skeptical about the value of digital format. Moreover, issues with quality, academic integrity, and the social aspects of learning continue to surface more and more. This might be the reason of focusing on technology too heavily without considering pedagogy as per said by Danilov et al. (2021).

However, digitalization of education is a long-term transformative process which cannot be reversed even in face of challenges. To ensure sustainability, higher education must count in the following three closely interconnected areas. First, teacher training is essential. Educators must be supported through workshops, mentorship, and continuous professional development. Second, inclusive access must remain a priority. Digital divide should be reduced with more investment in infrastructure by governments and institutions alike. Third, pedagogical innovation must be the driving force for digitalization. Technology should be used not for its novelty but for its ability to enhance learning outcomes. The ultimate goal is to enrich the existing education, not to erase traditional one.

In conclusion, the digitalization has redefined the whole system of higher education, presenting both opportunities and challenges. Innovative approaches such as gamification, artificial intelligence, and virtual reality are expanding the horizons of learning, whereas blended learning has emerged as a balance of traditional and digital modes of learning. At the same time, challenges we still have need an urgent attention and solution. By investing in

teacher development, promoting inclusivity, and ensuring that pedagogy guides technology, higher education can reach a sustainable digital future.

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YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA TIL TA’LIMI: YUTUQLAR VA MUAMMOLAR

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Anotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O‘zbekistonda til ta’limining holati, erishilgan yutuqlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari tahlil qilinadi. Shu jumladan, davlat tili va xorijiy tillar o‘qitilishidagi zamonaviy tendensiyalar, innovatsion yondashuvlar hamda til siyosatini takomillashtirish bo‘yicha g‘oyalar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Yangi O‘zbekistonda ta’lim islohotlari, til ta’limi, innovatsion texnologiyalar, CEFR, kommunikativ yondashuv, globalashuv, ko‘p tillilik, IELTS, ta’lim sifati, metodik baza, raqamli ta’lim.

Annotation: This article analyzes the current state of language education in Uzbekistan, the achievements made, existing challenges, and possible solutions. It also highlights modern trends in teaching the state and foreign languages, innovative approaches, and ideas for improving language policy.

Keywords: educational reforms in New Uzbekistan, language education, innovative technologies, CEFR, communicative approach, globalization, multilingualism, IELTS, quality of education, methodological base, digital education.

Bugungi kunda Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyotining muhim yo‘nalishlaridan biri -ta’lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilishdir. Ayniqsa, til ta’limi sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan o‘zgarishlar yosh avlodning dunyoqarashi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

So‘nggi yillarda chet tillarini o‘qitishga katta e’tibor qaratilmoqda. Maktabgacha ta’limdan boshlab oliy o‘quv yurtlarigacha ingliz, rus, koreys va boshqa tillar bosqichma-bosqich o‘qitilmoqda. “Chet tillarini o‘rganishni ommalashtirish” dasturi doirasida o‘qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, darsliklarni yangilash va interaktiv o‘qitish usullarini joriy etish ishlari amalga oshirilmoqda.

Bugungi kunda ko'plab maktablarda interaktiv metodlar, multimedia vositalari va onlayn platformalar (Quizlet, Duolingo, EduPage va boshqalar) yordamida darslar o'tilmoqda. Bu esa o'quvchilarning tilga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirmoqda. Shu bilan birga, CEFR tizimi asosida baholash joriy etilgani o'quvchilar bilimini xalqaro darajada aniqlash imkonini bermoqda.

Biroq til ta'limida hali ham ayrim muammolar mavjud. Ayrim hududlarda malakali o'qituvchilar yetishmaydi, darsliklar sifati hamma joyda bir xil emas. Qishloq maktablarida texnik jihozlar yetarli emasligi ham ta'lim jarayoniga ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda.

Shunga qaramay, islohotlar bosqichma-bosqich samara bermoqda. Yangi O'zbekiston yoshlari til o'rganish orqali keng dunyo eshiklarini ochmoqda. Tilni bilish -bugun nafaqat bilim, balki imkoniyat, muvaffaqiyat kalitiga aylanmoqda.

Til – millatning ruhi, madaniyatining asosi va tafakkurining ifodasidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi mustaqillikka erishgach, til siyosatini mustahkamlash, o'zbek tilining nufuzini oshirish, xorijiy tillarni o'rganish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishiga aylandi.

Yangi O'zbekiston davrida, ya'ni 2017-yildan boshlab, ta'lim tizimi tubdan isloh qilinib, til o'qitish jarayoni xalqaro tajriba asosida takomillashtirilmoqda. Prezidentimiz Sh.M. Mirziyoyev ta'kidlaganidek, "Yosh avlodning zamonaviy bilim va chet tillarini puxta egallashi -millat kelajagi garovidir."

So'nggi yillarda O'zbekiston hukumati til o'qitish sohasida qator islohotlarni amalga oshirdi. Xususan, 2020-yil 20-oktabrdagi 606-son qaror bilan "O'zbekiston Respublikasida Davlat tilini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi" qabul qilindi. Bu hujjat o'zbek tilining nafaqat ichki nufuzi, balki xalqaro miqyosdagi maqomini ham oshirishni ko'zda tutadi.

Shuningdek, 2019-yil 6-maydagi PF-5712-son Farmon chet tillarini o'qitishni tubdan isloh qildi. Bugungi kunda maktabgacha ta'limdan boshlab, oliy ta'limgacha bo'lgan barcha bosqichlarda chet tillarini o'rganish tizimi bosqichma-bosqich takomillashmoqda.

Chet tillar bo'yicha CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) tizimi joriy etildi. Bu yondashuv o'quvchilarning til bilish darajasini xalqaro standartlar asosida baholash imkonini beradi.

O'zbek tili bo'yicha esa "Davlat tili kuni", "Til haftaliklari", "Ona tilim -g'ururim" kabi loyihalar orqali yoshlarning ona tiliga hurmatini oshirishga erishildi. Til o'qitish metodikasi sohasida yangi darsliklar, interaktiv elektron qo'llanmalar va audio-video materiallar yaratilmoqda. Shuningdek, raqamli ta'lim rivojlanib, "EduMarket", "UzLingvo", "ZiyoNet", "MyELT" kabi platformalarda onlayn darslar, testlar va o'quv resurslari keng qo'llanilmoqda. Natijada o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'rganish imkoniyatlari kengaydi.

Til ta'limi -bu o'quvchilarda tilni bilish, tushunish, nutqda qo'llay olish, yozma va og'zaki muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan o'quv-tarbiyaviy jarayondir. Til ta'limi ona tili, chet tili yoki davlat tili bo'yicha olib borilishi mumkin.

Yutuqlar faqat xorijiy tillar bilan cheklanmaydi. Yangi O'zbekistonda ona tili va davlat tili mavqeini yuksaltirishga ham katta e'tibor berilmoqda. "Davlat tili haqida"gi qonunning yangilanishi, o'zbek tilida ilmiy va adabiy asarlarni yaratish, hamda rasmiy idoralarda davlat tilida ish yuritishni kengaytirish -muhim natijalardan biridir.

Yangi O'zbekiston davrida til ta'limi sohasida tub islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Mamlakatda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish, o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, darsliklar va metodik bazani yangilash bo'yicha muhim yutuqlarga erishildi. CEFR, IELTS kabi xalqaro standartlar ta'lim tizimiga bosqichma-bosqich joriy qilinayotgani esa o'quvchilarning til kompetensiyasini xalqaro darajada baholash imkonini bermoqda.

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LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN - ACHIEVEMENTS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: In recent years, Uzbekistan has gone through major reforms in educational field, especially in terms of language acquisition. These reforms have been designed to develop foreign language teaching skills, especially English language in accordance with international standards. This article analyzes both the main achievements and the current problems in education system of Uzbekistan. In addition, it demonstrates the role of modern technology, the development of teachers' experience as well as the creation of a multilingual learning environment.

Key words: multilingualism, innovation, experience of teachers, quality of education.

In the age of globalization, language is an important factor of indicating competitiveness. Therefore, language education has become a strategic priority in the “New Uzbekistan” strategy. In fact, Presidential Decree PQ-5117 from May 19, 2021 “On measures to systematize the teaching of foreign languages” marked a turning point in this field. The decree introduced reforms aimed at improving teaching methods while establishing clear proficiency standards as well as enhancing teacher qualifications.

According to UNESCO (2022), Uzbekistan’s recent educational policy has emphasized multilingualism and inclusive access where English is selected as a tool for international integration and career mobility.

What is more, The Common European Framework of Reference for Language (CEFR) has become a foundation for assessing language proficiency in Uzbekistan, having been adapted to local educational system. According to Rakhmonova (2023), CEFR-based curricula are now implemented throughout state schools and higher education institutions. This, admittedly, allowed language levels of learners to be measured in accordance with international standards. Hence, the Global Research Network found that teacher training programs in Samarkand and Tashkent now align with CEFR framework, which has significantly improved teaching consistency and transparency across different regions in Uzbekistan.

Foreign language instruction now begins from preschool level, one of the recent key innovations of educational reform. The programs such as “A Million Coders” and “Speak English” aim to provide young learners with early exposure to English and digital literacy. The Ministry of Preschool and School Education (2023) reports that over 60% of public schools have introduced foreign language clubs or online learning programs in cooperation with platforms like BBC Learning English, Coursera and Duolingo. Furthermore, the national certification system for teachers and students launched in 2024 currently recognizes international qualifications like IELTS and TOEFL, encouraging learners to meet global standards.

In conclusion, the education system has undergone fundamental changes in the past few years. In fact, reforms being introduced gradually and mentioned above such as teacher retraining have truly led to measurable progress. To overcome remaining challenges as of teacher experience or quality of learning resources, continuous support by all structural systems is essential. If languages continue to be supported and integrated into education and technology, Uzbekistan’s language policy will achieve sustainable and globally recognized success.

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THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. The article examines the key theoretical and practical issues of equivalence in translation between Uzbek and English. In fact, equivalence means that the translation conveys the same meaning, style, and emotional effect as the original text. However, due to significant grammatical, cultural, and lexical differences between the two languages, achieving full equivalence is often challenging. Therefore, the concept of equivalence, its main types, and real examples of translation difficulties are outlined in this article. It also describes strategies that translators may use to solve these problems and ensure accurate and culturally appropriate translations.

Key words: translation equivalence; Uzbek–English translation; dynamic equivalence; formal equivalence; linguistic differences; cultural translation; translation strategies

Translation is the process of transferring meaning from one language into another. Indeed, one of the core goals in translation is achieving equivalence, meaning the translated text should deliver the same message and emotional impact as the original. However, this goal is difficult to reach, especially between two linguistically and culturally distant languages such as Uzbek and English. Uzbek, being considered as a Turkic language with agglutinative

grammar, and English - a Germanic analytic language, differ in both structure and worldview. These differences make direct, word-for-word translation nearly impossible. As Nida (1964) emphasized, translators should prioritize meaning and communicative effect over literal accuracy. Thus, both the theoretical foundations and practical challenges of equivalence between Uzbek and English will be discussed further.

Equivalence refers to the relationship between source and target texts where the translation conveys the same meaning, style, and communicative function. Jakobson (1959) noted that complete equivalence between languages is rare; translators must find approximate meaning rather than identical wording, whereas Nida (1964) distinguished between formal equivalence (literal, form-based translation) and dynamic equivalence (meaning- and effect-based translation). Dynamic equivalence is often more suitable for Uzbek–English translation because it focuses more on the reader’s response.

Similarly, Newmark (1988) described two translation methods: semantic translation, focusing on the original meaning, and communicative translation, focusing on the effect on the target audience. The translator’s choice depends on the purpose, audience, and text type.

Many Uzbek words have no direct English equivalent. For example, *mehmondo‘stlik* expresses deep hospitality and generosity that cannot really be expressed with the English word *hospitality*. Ganieva (2020) explained that such cultural concepts often require paraphrasing or short explanations to preserve meaning. Furthermore, Baker (1992) recommended using paraphrase or descriptive phrases when no single equivalent exists. Idioms and Proverbs - Idioms and proverbs are culture-bound expressions that rarely translate literally. Example:

Uzbek: Ko‘z qorachig‘iday asramoq

Word-for-word in English: To protect like the pupil of the eye

Better translation: To cherish or To protect dearly

Khalilova (2021) emphasized that idioms carry deep emotional meaning; translators should use equivalent English idioms or explanatory phrases. Akhmedova (2022) also showed how Uzbek proverbs can be translated using either similar English expressions or brief explanations.

Style and Formality - Uzbek literature and official documents often use poetic or formal tones. Literal translation into English can sound unnatural. As Hatim and Mason (1997) explained, translators should adjust style and formality to suit the expectations of English readers while maintaining the original tone.

Translators apply several strategies to overcome these challenges. Vinay and Darbelnet (1995) proposed key methods: Borrowing: Using the same word (e.g., *Navro‘z*). Transposition: Changing grammatical form (noun → verb). Modulation: Changing perspective to express meaning naturally. Adaptation: Replacing a cultural reference with a similar one. Baker (1992) also discussed compensation, where meaning lost in one part is restored elsewhere. For instance, the Uzbek greeting *Choy iching!* (“Drink tea!”) can be translated as “Would you like some tea?”-maintaining the polite hospitality implied in Uzbek culture.

Equivalence in translation aims to preserve meaning and emotional impact across languages. However, between Uzbek and English, perfect equivalence is rare due to structural, grammatical, and cultural differences. Scholars such as Nida (1964), Jakobson (1959), Newmark (1988), and Baker (1992) have provided valuable frameworks for addressing these challenges. As researchers like Ganieva (2020) and Khudoyberganova (2018) have shown, successful translation between Uzbek and English requires not only

linguistic knowledge but also cultural sensitivity. Translators must select the most appropriate strategy to preserve message, tone, and style. With proper understanding and creativity, a high level of equivalence can be achieved, even if perfect equivalence is unattainable.

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THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC PLANNING IN ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES

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Abstract: Strategic planning has become an indispensable component of effective educational management in the twenty-first century. It enables educational institutions to define long-term goals, align resources with priorities, and monitor progress toward measurable learning outcomes. This article examines the significance of strategic planning in improving educational quality, institutional performance, and student achievement. Drawing on contemporary research in educational leadership and policy, it argues that systematic planning fosters accountability, innovation, and sustainable development in education. The study concludes that successful implementation of strategic planning requires collaboration among stakeholders, data-driven decision-making, and continuous evaluation.

Keywords: strategic planning, educational outcomes, leadership, quality assurance, innovation, sustainability

Strategic planning is widely recognized as a cornerstone of modern educational administration. It refers to a systematic process through which institutions set goals, determine actions, and allocate resources to achieve desired outcomes (Bryson, 2021). In the context of education, strategic planning provides a framework for aligning instructional practices, human capital, and institutional priorities with broader national or global educational objectives. In many countries, the rapid pace of social, economic, and technological change has compelled educational systems to become more adaptive and evidence-based. Schools and universities are now expected not only to provide quality

instruction but also to demonstrate accountability and measurable progress (Fullan, 2021). Hence, strategic planning has evolved from a managerial function into an essential leadership tool that guides long-term improvement and innovation in learning environments.

The Concept and Principles of Strategic Planning in Education: strategic planning in education combines theoretical frameworks from organizational management and educational leadership. It involves identifying institutional missions, assessing internal and external environments, formulating strategies, and evaluating results (Poister et al., 2020). Unlike short-term operational planning, strategic planning focuses on sustainability and continuous improvement.

The principles of effective strategic planning include participation, evidence-based decision-making, flexibility, and transparency. Inclusive participation ensures that administrators, teachers, students, and community members collectively shape institutional goals (Hallinger, 2020). Evidence-based decision-making relies on data analytics, assessment results, and research to guide policy directions. Flexibility allows institutions to adapt to emerging trends such as digital transformation or curriculum reform, while transparency enhances trust and accountability among stakeholders.

A well-designed strategic plan typically encompasses several stages:

1. Situational analysis - identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT).
2. Goal formulation - establishing measurable and time-bound objectives.
3. Strategy implementation - assigning responsibilities and mobilizing resources.
4. Monitoring and evaluation - assessing progress and revising strategies accordingly (Bryson, 2021).

By adhering to these principles, educational institutions can create a coherent vision that integrates academic excellence with social responsibility.

Strategic planning as a driver of educational quality and innovation: strategic planning directly influences the quality of education by promoting systematic improvement and innovation. According to Bush (2020), schools with well-articulated strategic plans demonstrate higher performance levels because their activities are purposefully aligned with institutional objectives. Strategic planning establishes performance indicators for teaching, learning, and administration, thereby creating a culture of accountability.

Furthermore, strategic planning encourages innovation in curriculum design, pedagogy, and assessment. When institutions conduct environmental scans and stakeholder consultations, they identify emerging educational needs-such as digital literacy or global citizenship-and incorporate them into strategic goals (OECD, 2022). This process ensures that education remains relevant and responsive to societal demands.

In higher education, strategic planning has become essential for internationalization and competitiveness. Universities use strategic frameworks to enhance research productivity, attract global partnerships, and integrate technology-based learning systems (Altbach & de Wit, 2020). Strategic approaches to digitalization-such as establishing e-learning centers or adopting hybrid instruction-demonstrate how planned innovation can lead to improved student engagement and achievement.

Moreover, strategic planning contributes to equity and inclusion by addressing disparities in educational access and outcomes. Institutions that use disaggregated data can identify underrepresented groups and develop targeted support programs (UNESCO, 2023). Thus, strategic planning serves not only as a managerial process but also as a moral imperative to ensure fairness and social justice in education.

Implementation and Challenges of Strategic Planning in Education: despite its benefits, the implementation of strategic planning in education faces several challenges. These include

insufficient leadership capacity, lack of stakeholder commitment, limited data infrastructure, and resource constraints (Harris & Jones, 2021). Effective strategic planning requires visionary leadership that can balance long-term goals with immediate institutional needs.

Leadership plays a critical role in translating strategic objectives into actionable steps. Transformational leaders inspire staff and students by communicating a clear vision, fostering collaboration, and encouraging innovation (Leithwood & Sun, 2020). Moreover, the establishment of monitoring and evaluation systems is crucial for tracking progress and ensuring accountability. Data-driven evaluation helps identify gaps between planned and actual outcomes, enabling timely adjustments (Poister et al., 2020).

Another significant challenge involves the sustainability of strategic plans. Many institutions develop comprehensive documents but fail to integrate them into everyday operations. To overcome this, strategic planning must become an ongoing, iterative process rather than a one-time administrative exercise (Bryson, 2021). Regular reviews, feedback mechanisms, and stakeholder participation help maintain the relevance and impact of the plan.

Finally, the success of strategic planning depends on an institutions organizational culture. A culture that values reflection, teamwork, and continuous learning provides fertile ground for effective strategy implementation. Professional development programs can equip educators with the necessary skills to engage in strategic thinking and contribute meaningfully to institutional growth (Fullan, 2021).

To conclude, strategic planning is more than a bureaucratic requirement; it is a transformative process that aligns vision, policy, and practice to enhance educational outcomes. By integrating evidence-based decision-making, stakeholder participation, and continuous evaluation, institutions can achieve higher levels of quality, innovation, and equity. The future of education depends on strategic foresight-the ability of leaders and educators to anticipate change and respond proactively. When properly executed, strategic planning becomes a dynamic mechanism for achieving academic excellence, social inclusion, and institutional sustainability. Therefore, fostering strategic thinking among all educational actors remains a key priority for achieving meaningful and lasting improvement.

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YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA CHET TILINI O‘QITISHDA MUSTAQIL TA’LIM MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDAGI MUAOMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yangi O‘zbekistondagi chet tili o‘qitish jarayonida o‘quvchilarni mustaqil ta’lim olish madaniyatni shakllantirishdagi muammoli holatlari va uning yechimlari bayon etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: motivatsiya, globallashuv, resurs, peer learning (do‘stlar bilan mashg‘ulot o‘tkazish yoki fikr almashish)

Annotation: This article discusses the problematic aspects of developing students’ independent learning culture in the process of teaching foreign languages in New Uzbekistan and proposes possible solutions.

Keywords: motivation, globalization, resource, peer learning (studying or sharing ideas with friends)

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются проблемные аспекты формирования культуры самостоятельного обучения учащихся в процессе преподавания иностранных языков в Новом Узбекистане, а также предлагаются пути их решения.

Ключевие слова: мотивация, глобализация, ресурс, peer learning (проведения занятий или обмен мнениями с друзьями)

Bugungi zamonaviy globallashuv jarayonida chet tillarini o'rganish judayam tez suratda o'sib bormoqda. Chet tilini bilish nafaqat shaxsiy rivojlanish, balki mamlakatning xalqaro maydondagi raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlaydigan muhim omillardan biridir. Shu sababdan ham ta'limning avvalgi bosqichlaridan boshlab yoshlarni chet tillarini o'rgatishga e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Muhtaram Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev tomonidan qabul qilingan "Chet tillarini o'rganishni ommalashtirish" [1,240] tog'risidagi qonun ham buning yaqqol misolidir. Xususan ta'lim tizimida chet tillarini o'qitish bo'yicha zamonaviy o'quv dasturlari ham ishlanib kun sayin o'quvchilarga va o'qituvchilarga tatbiq qilinmoqda. Erta ta'limdan boshlab sifatli ta'limni yo'lga qo'yish Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasining ajralmas qismiga aylandi. Yuqoridagi bir qancha omillarga qaramay, chet tilini o'rganishdagi mustaqil ta'limning madaniyatini hali ham shakllantirish muhimligini yaqqol namoyon bo'layotganiga guvoh bo'lamiz va chet tilini o'rganishda mustaqil ta'lim olish madaniyatini shakllantirish dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

Chet tilini mustaqil o'rganish madaniyati-bu shaxsning o'z bilim olish jarayonini ongli ravishda to'g'ri tashkil etishi, maqsad qo'yishi, rejalashtirish, o'zini baholay olishi va o'rganishga doimiy rag'bat hosil qila olishidir. Professor va lingvist Kranshen "Mustaqil o'rganish-bu shaxsning ichki nazorati, ya'ni inson o'z bilim jarayonining rahbariga aylanganda haqiqiy o'qish boshlanadi". Kranshen fikricha ya'ni, o'quvchini o'qishga majbur qilib bo'lmaydi, uni ilhomlantirish, qiziqtirish va erkinlik berish orqali haqiqiy natijaga erishiladi. [2,62]

Ko'plab o'quvchilar va o'rganuvchilar orasida chet tilini o'rganishga ichki rag'bat yetishmayabdi sababi ularni faqat imtihon topshirish, sertifikat olish va talabni bajarish bilan cheklanish sodir bo'lmoqda. Bu esa o'rganish jarayonini ichki ehtiyojdan emas, tashqi bosimdan kelib chiqqadigan faoliyatga olib kelishi mumkin. Natijada barqaroq o'rganish sodir bo'lmaydi va chet tilini o'rganish madaniyatiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bunga misol tariqasida yana Kranshen "Motivatsiyasi kuchli shaxs o'z ustida ishlashdan charchamaydi, chunki u natijani boshqalarga emas, o'ziga isbotlamoqchi bo'ladi". [2,124] O'quvchilar o'rganish rejasini tuzish, vaqtni to'g'ri taqsimlash va o'z faoliyatini tahlil qiliishga odatlanmagan. Bu esa mustaqil ta'lim madaniyatining asosiga zid holatda o'zini nazorat qilishni kamaytiradi. Ko'plab o'quvchilar chet tilini o'rganishni faqatgina "O'qitish kurs'lariga borish bilan cheklanib, o'z shaxsiy o'rganish tizimini shakllantirmaydilar va bu esa faqat o'qituvchiga to'liq tayanish holatini kuchaytiradi. Arab yozuvchisi Abu G'uddaning "Ilm olish sirlari" da shunday ma'noli jumlani keltirgan; "Ustoz-yo'l ko'rsatuvchi, ammo yo'lni bosib o'tuvchi o'zi bo'lishi kerak". [3,196] Demak, o'quvchi mustaqil o'rganishga odatlanmasa, ustozning mehnati ham to'liq samara bermaydi.

Raqamli davrda o'rganish uchun imkoniyatlar ko'p bo'lsa-da, ularni to'g'ri foydalanish madaniyati hali hanuz odamlar orasida muammo bo'lib qolmoqda yoki past darajada. Misol tariqasida onlayn platformalari (Coursera, BBC learning English, Duolingo) to'liq omma orasida o'zlashtirilmagan, mobil ilovalar orqali o'rganishda izchilikni saqlamaydi, internetdagi materiallarni to'g'ri tanlab olib o'rganish ko'nimasiga ega emas.

Yangi Ozbekistonda chet tilini o'rganishda asosiy muammo-bu mustaqil o'rganish madaniyatining to'liq shakllanmaganligidir. Bu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun avvalo, o'quvchilarda ichki motivatsiyani kuchaytirish; metakognitiv ko'nikmalarni (o'zini kuzatish, baholash, tahlil qilish) to'liq rivojlantirish (raqamli ta'lim madaniyatini oshirish); o'quvchi shaxsini o'rganish jarayonining markaziga qo'yishi zarurdir. Va so'z oxirida "Ilm olish sirlari" kitobidan yana bir iqtibos keltiramiz "Kim ilmni mustaqil o'rganishga odatlansa, u umrining har daqiqasida yangi ma'no topadi." [3,54-55] Albatta, bu fikr ham chet tilini mustaqil o'rganishda madaniyat shakllanishiga shior bo'lib qolsa ajab emas.

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STUDYING ABROAD IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION: PATHWAYS TO INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE AND PERSONAL GROWTH

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Annotation. Writing a scientific article is a fundamental skill for researchers, as it enables them to contribute to their academic discipline, gain professional recognition, and advance their careers. A well-structured article not only communicates new findings but also fosters academic discourse and facilitates the dissemination of knowledge. This paper examines the essential components of writing a scholarly article, including research methodologies, structural organization, and the critical elements necessary for effective academic writing.

Keywords: Studying abroad, globalization, international education, cultural adaptability, intercultural competence, personal growth, independence, resilience, problem-solving skills, language acquisition, language immersion, communication skills, career advantages, employability, cross-cultural communication, multinational corporations, innovative thinking, creativity.

Аннотация. Написание научной статьи - основополагающий навык для исследователей, поскольку он позволяет им вносить вклад в развитие своей академической дисциплины, получать профессиональное признание и продвигаться по карьерной лестнице. Хорошо структурированная статья не только сообщает о новых открытиях, но и способствует академическому дискурсу и распространению знаний. В данной работе рассматриваются основные компоненты написания научной статьи, включая методологии исследования, структурную организацию и критические элементы, необходимые для эффективного академического письма.

Ключевые слова: Обучение за рубежом, глобализация, международное образование, культурная адаптация, межкультурная компетентность, личностный рост, независимость, стрессоустойчивость, навыки решения проблем, усвоение языка, языковое погружение, коммуникативные навыки, карьерные преимущества, трудоустройство, межкультурная коммуникация, многонациональные корпорации, инновационное мышление, креативность.

Annotatsiya: Ilmiy maqola yozish tadqiqotchilar uchun asosiy mahoratdir, chunki bu ularga o‘z ilmiy intizomiga hissa qo‘shish, professional e’tirofga ega bo‘lish va o‘z martabasini oshirish imkonini beradi. Yaxshi tuzilgan maqola nafaqat yangi topilmalar haqida ma’lumot beradi, balki akademik nutqni rag‘batlantiradi va bilimlarni tarqatishni osonlashtiradi. Ushbu maqola ilmiy maqola yozishning muhim tarkibiy qismlarini, jumladan tadqiqot metodologiyalari, tizimli tashkil etish va samarali akademik yozish uchun zarur bo‘lgan muhim elementlarni o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Chet elda o‘qish, globallashtirish, xalqaro ta’lim, madaniy moslashuvchanlik, madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya, shaxsiy o‘shirish, mustaqillik, qat’iyatlilik,

muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatlari, tillarni o'zlashtirish, tilga singib ketish, muloqot qobiliyatlari, martaba afzalliklari, ishga joylashish, madaniyatlararo muloqot, ko'p millatli korporatsiyalar, innovatsion fikrlash, ijodkorlik.

Studying abroad is a transformative experience that provides students with significant academic, professional, and personal benefits. In an era of increasing globalization, international education plays a pivotal role in fostering cultural adaptability, language proficiency, and enhanced career prospects. This paper explores the multifaceted advantages of studying abroad, including the development of cultural competence, personal growth, independence, problem-solving skills, innovative thinking, and language acquisition. Each section is supported by scholarly literature and empirical examples, demonstrating the long-term value of international education in a rapidly interconnected world.

The ongoing process of globalization has heightened the demand for individuals with international experience and cross-cultural competencies. Studying abroad provides students with unique opportunities to engage in immersive learning environments, fostering both academic and personal development. According to the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Uzbekistan's policy of openness, its active entry into the global market, and the expansion of international cooperation in all fields are increasing the need for foreign language proficiency." This underscores the growing importance of international education in equipping students with the skills required to succeed in the modern global economy.

This paper examines the core benefits of studying abroad, emphasizing its impact on cultural adaptability, personal and intellectual growth, independence, problem-solving capabilities, language acquisition, and career advancement.

Cultural Adaptability

One of the most profound benefits of studying abroad is the enhancement of cultural adaptability. Exposure to diverse cultures, traditions, and social norms enables students to develop cultural sensitivity and intercultural competence. Hofstede (2001) highlights that cultural awareness is critical for effective engagement in an interconnected world. Similarly, Paige et al. (2009) assert that students who study abroad demonstrate improved intercultural competence, which facilitates their ability to navigate diverse environments.

Empirical studies support these claims. For instance, participants in the European Union's Erasmus+ program report increased cultural sensitivity and adaptability upon returning to their home countries. Hammer et al. (2003) developed the Intercultural Development Inventory (IDI), which measures intercultural sensitivity, and their research indicates that students who engage in international education show significant growth in their ability to understand and engage with cultural differences.

Living in a foreign country fosters personal development by promoting resilience, self-reliance, and emotional maturity. Chirkov and Ryan (2001) argue that studying abroad enhances psychological autonomy, as students must navigate new social and academic environments independently.

For example, international students in Japan are required to adapt to a demanding academic culture while simultaneously managing daily responsibilities. This process cultivates resilience and independence. Moreover, Tian and Lowe (2013) found that international education encourages self-reflection, emotional intelligence, and adaptability-skills that are crucial for personal and professional success.

Studying abroad requires students to solve complex problems and make independent decisions. The need to navigate unfamiliar bureaucratic, social, and academic environments fosters critical thinking and the capacity for independent decision-making (Inkson et al., 1997).

For instance, international students in Germany must manage complex administrative processes, such as securing residency permits and healthcare coverage. Successfully addressing these challenges enhances their ability to identify problems, evaluate potential solutions, and implement effective strategies. Such experiences not only foster intellectual independence but also prepare students to manage ambiguity and uncertainty in professional contexts.

Language immersion is a crucial advantage of studying abroad, as it accelerates language acquisition and enhances communication skills. Krashen's (1982) Input Hypothesis suggests that natural language learning occurs more effectively in immersive contexts. Daily engagement with native speakers promotes fluency and cultural literacy.

For example, students studying in France improve their language proficiency through consistent interaction with local communities. Coleman (1997) found that language learners in immersive settings exhibit superior linguistic competence compared to those in traditional classroom environments. Furthermore, these communication skills extend beyond linguistic proficiency, enhancing students' ability to engage in cross-cultural dialogue—a critical skill in multinational work environments.

Employers increasingly value international experience due to the unique skill sets it cultivates. Crossman and Clarke (2010) argue that study-abroad graduates possess enhanced employability owing to their cross-cultural communication skills and global perspectives.

Case studies further highlight this advantage. Graduates from the London School of Economics (LSE) with international education experience are often recruited by global corporations due to their adaptability and intercultural competence. Additionally, Inkson et al. (1997) contend that exposure to international environments fosters adaptability—an attribute that is highly valued by multinational employers.

Managing personal finances while studying abroad enhances financial literacy and budgeting skills. Students must navigate complex financial processes, including currency exchange, international banking, and managing living expenses.

For instance, international students in Canada often balance part-time work with academic commitments, fostering an understanding of financial planning and responsibility. Such experiences equip students with essential financial management skills that are transferable to their future professional lives.

International education provides access to extensive professional networks, fostering career development. Universities frequently organize networking events, industry conferences, and collaborative research projects that connect students with global professionals.

Studying abroad enhances innovative thinking and creativity by exposing students to diverse perspectives and problem-solving approaches. Maddux and Galinsky (2009) found that individuals who experience cultural diversity demonstrate greater cognitive flexibility and creative problem-solving abilities.

For instance, students participating in interdisciplinary research initiatives in the United States often develop innovative solutions to global challenges by integrating diverse academic methodologies. Exposure to new cultural frameworks promotes creative thinking, which is essential for success in today's knowledge-based economy.

Studying abroad offers a comprehensive range of academic, personal, and professional benefits. It fosters cultural adaptability, enhances language proficiency, promotes personal growth, and equips students with practical skills such as financial management and problem-solving. Furthermore, international education strengthens professional networks, enhances employability, and fosters innovative thinking.

As globalization accelerates, the ability to navigate diverse environments and demonstrate cross-cultural competence remains crucial. Therefore, investing in study-abroad programs is not only beneficial for individual students but also for society as a whole, fostering a generation of adaptable, innovative, and globally-minded professionals.

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THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines the development of language education in New Uzbekistan with a focus on its achievements and challenges. It discusses the reforms in the education system, the implementation of innovative teaching methods, and the use of digital technologies in language learning. The paper also highlights the problems that still exist, such as teacher preparedness and unequal access to resources, and offers recommendations for further improvement.

Keywords: language education, New Uzbekistan, achievements, challenges, innovation, teaching reform.

Introduction: In recent years, Uzbekistan has undergone large-scale transformations in all spheres, including education. The development of language education has become one of the country's strategic priorities. The ability to communicate in several languages is viewed as a key factor in global competitiveness and cultural openness. The government of New Uzbekistan has implemented numerous reforms aimed at improving the quality of teaching and promoting foreign language learning. Presidential decrees, new curricula, and teacher training programs have played an important role in this process. These changes are designed to create a new generation of specialists who are fluent in Uzbek and at least one foreign language.

The modernization of language education in New Uzbekistan can be seen in several directions. First, the curriculum has been updated to align with international standards such as the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). This alignment allows teachers to plan lessons more effectively and helps students measure their progress

accurately. Second, digitalization has significantly influenced the teaching process. Interactive whiteboards, online courses, and multimedia resources have made language learning more interesting and efficient. Many schools and universities now use digital platforms to conduct tests, share materials, and organize virtual classes. Third, teacher development has become a priority. Hundreds of teachers participate in professional training programs both inside and outside the country. [1] They learn new pedagogical strategies such as task-based learning, communicative methods, and student-centered approaches. These methods focus on real-life language use and practical communication skills rather than memorization. Despite these successes, several challenges remain. Some rural schools still lack access to modern equipment and the internet. Teachers in remote areas often have limited opportunities for professional growth. In addition, students' motivation varies-while many are enthusiastic about learning languages, others still see it as a requirement rather than a personal goal. Another issue is material quality. Some textbooks and online resources are outdated or not adapted to local contexts. Improving the content of teaching materials and making them culturally relevant is necessary. Furthermore, assessment systems should focus not only on grammar and vocabulary but also on communication and critical thinking skills. To address these issues, continuous investment in education is essential. Schools should be equally provided with digital resources, and teachers should receive ongoing methodological support. Encouraging creativity, organizing language clubs, and using real-life projects can also enhance students' motivation and practical skills.

Moreover, one of the most important aspects of language education in New Uzbekistan is the promotion of multilingualism. Today, not only English but also Russian, Chinese, Turkish, and Korean languages are gaining popularity among students. This tendency shows that young people are becoming more open-minded and ready to participate in international communication. Learning several foreign languages helps students broaden their worldview and understand different cultures, which is essential in the modern globalized world. Another significant step is the introduction of early language learning. Foreign languages are now taught from the first grades of school. This early start helps children develop listening and speaking skills naturally and increases their confidence in using another language. Many schools have also established language clubs and debate societies where students can practice communication in a friendly and motivating environment.

In addition, the cooperation between universities and international educational organizations has strengthened. Exchange programs, online conferences, and joint research projects give teachers and students the opportunity to share experiences and learn from foreign specialists. Such initiatives help to integrate Uzbekistan's education system into the global academic community and ensure the continuous development of teaching quality.

However, for these achievements to be sustainable, it is necessary to continue improving educational infrastructure. The modernization of libraries, creation of digital learning platforms, and access to authentic materials should become a long-term priority. Besides, more attention should be paid to the psychological aspects of learning - encouraging students' curiosity, reducing anxiety, and building a positive classroom atmosphere. In the future, the main goal of language education in New Uzbekistan should be not only to teach grammar or vocabulary but also to develop communicative competence, intercultural understanding, and creative thinking. By combining traditional teaching methods with modern innovations, the country can prepare a generation that is not only knowledgeable but also globally competitive and culturally aware. [2]

Incentives and Motivation Policies: Recent presidential decrees in Uzbekistan have introduced several incentives to support foreign language teachers. Educators who obtain

international certificates such as IELTS, CEFR, or TESOL receive a salary bonus of 40–50 percent. In addition, schools are now provided with funds - up to one million soums - to purchase modern textbooks and teaching materials.[1]

Moreover, a new policy requires all foreign language teachers to hold either a national or international qualification certificate to continue their professional activities. Over the next three years, it is planned that around 53,000 teachers across the country will complete certification programs. These measures aim to ensure higher teaching quality, encourage continuous self-development, and recognize teachers' professional achievements.[4]

Uzbekistan is also planning to transition from an 11-year to a 12-year general education system. This reform is designed to bring the national education structure closer to international standards and to help graduates enter universities without the need for an additional foundation year.

The new structure will allow foreign languages to be taught more consistently and at earlier stages of education. Starting language learning from the first grades and maintaining a gradual progression throughout all school years will create a stronger linguistic base. This step is expected to significantly improve students' fluency, expand their global opportunities, and make the education system more competitive at the international level.[3]

Language education in New Uzbekistan has reached a new level of development. The reforms have contributed to a stronger educational foundation, better teacher training, and increased student engagement. However, challenges such as unequal access to resources, lack of teacher readiness, and limited motivation still need to be solved. The future success of language education depends on cooperation among educators, policymakers, and researchers. By promoting innovation, strengthening international collaboration, and maintaining consistent quality improvement, Uzbekistan can build a modern and competitive language education system that meets global standards.

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FILMLAR VA SERIALLAR ORQALI TIL O'RGANISHNING SAMARASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada filmlar va seriallar orqali chet tilini o'rganishning samaradorligi ilmiy jihatdan yoritilgan. Audiovizual vositalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning tilni tabiiy muhitda o'zlashtirishiga, so'z boyligini kengaytirishga, tinglab tushunish va talaffuz ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilishi ta'kidlangan. Shuningdek, kino mahsulotlari orqali madaniy bilimlarni oshirish, o'quvchilarda motivatsiya va qiziqishni kuchaytirish imkoniyatlari ko'rsatib berilgan. Maqolada filmlardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ham bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, film, serial, subtitr, nutqiy ko'nikma, talaffuz, madaniyat.

Annotation: This article scientifically highlights the effectiveness of learning a foreign language through films and TV series. It emphasizes that the use of audiovisual materials helps learners acquire the language in a natural environment, expand their vocabulary, and develop listening comprehension and pronunciation skills. Moreover, it demonstrates how cinematic content can enhance cultural knowledge and increase students' motivation and interest. The article also provides practical recommendations for the effective use of films in language learning.

Keywords: foreign language, film, TV series, subtitles, speaking skills, pronunciation, culture.

Hozirgi globallashtirish davrida xorijiy tillarni mukammal bilish insonning shaxsiy va kasbiy raqobatbardoshligini belgilovchi muhim omilga aylanmoqda. Tillarni o'rganish jarayonida turli metodlar mavjud bo'lsa-da, so'nggi yillarda filmlar va seriallardan ta'limiy vosita sifatida foydalanish keng tarqalmoqda. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchilarda o'rganish jarayonini qiziqarli va samarali tashkil etish imkonini beradi, ularni sun'iy o'quv muhiti emas, balki tabiiy til muhitiga yaqinlashtiradi, shu orqali nutqiy ko'nikmalarni yanada tezroq rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Ayni paytda, xorijiy tillarni o'zlashtirish nafaqat bugungi kunda, balki insoniyat tarixi davomida ham muhim ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va madaniy ahamiyat kasb etib kelgan. Tillarni o'rganish mamlakatlar o'rtasida diplomatik munosabatlar o'rnatish, madaniy hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish, savdo-sotiqni rivojlantirish va turli sohalarida tajriba almashishda asosiy vositalardan biri bo'lib xizmat qilgan. Ona tilidan tashqari boshqa tilni egallash insonning dunyoqarashini kengaytiradi, turli xalqlarning madaniy merosi, urf-odatlarini, tarixiy taraqqiyoti va qadriyatlarini o'rganish imkonini yaratadi. Natijada o'quvchi nafaqat shaxsiy bilim doirasini boyitadi, balki yashab turgan hududining ijtimoiy va madaniy taraqqiyotiga ham hissa qo'shadi.

O'zbekiston tarixiga murojaat qilar ekanmiz, mamlakat qadimdan geografik joylashuvi bois g'arb va sharq madaniyatlari kesishgan hudud sifatida shakllanganini ko'rish mumkin. Buyuk Ipak yo'li chorrahasida joylashganligi sababli bu hudud ilm-fan, savdo va madaniyat markazlaridan biri sifatida shakllandi. Uzoq yillar davomida nafaqat islomiy dunyo, balki butun mintaqa uchun ilmiy markaz bo'lgan O'zbekiston hududlarida turli elatlar yashagan va ular o'zaro muloqot qilishga majbur bo'lgan. Bu esa turli tillarni o'rganish ehtiyojini keltirib chiqargan. Bugungi globallashtirish sharoitida ham xorijiy tillarni bilish

davlatlararo aloqalar, xalqaro hamkorlik va shaxsiy muvaffaqiyatlar uchun zarur shartga aylangan. Shu bois, chet tillarni o'rganish hozirgi davrda yanada dolzarbdir.

Chet tilini o'rganish jarayoni ko'pchilik uchun murakkab vazifa bo'lib, bu haqiqat hech kimga sir emas. Chunki xorijiy tilni o'zlashtirish nafaqat intellektual mehnatni, balki sabr-toqat, qat'iyat va muntazam mashqni ham talab etadi. Tadqiqotchilarning ta'kidlashicha, "chet tilini o'rganish inson miyasidagi eng qiyin faoliyat turlaridan biridir. Chunki bunda ona tilidagi lingvistik shakl va qoliplarni boshqa tilga oddiygina o'girish bilan cheklanib qolmaydi, balki o'sha til doirasida mustaqil ravishda fikrlash ko'nikmasini shakllantirish zarur bo'ladi".

Shuningdek, chet tillarini o'rganishdagi eng katta muammolardan yana biri – barcha o'quvchilar uchun yagona, hamma uchun mos keladigan universal metodikaning mavjud emasligidir. O'quvchilarning ona tili, dunyoqarashi, tilni o'rganishdagi qobiliyatlari va maqsadlaridan kelib chiqib, har biriga individual uslub tanlash talab etiladi. Tilni o'zlashtirishda grammatik qoidalar, imlo va talaffuz me'yorlari, lug'at boyligini kengaytirish muhim bo'lsa-da, ularning o'zi yetarli emas. Chunki chet tilini mukammal bilish uchun faqat til tizimini emas, balki o'sha til sohiblarining turmush tarzi, urf-odatlari, milliy mentaliteti, xalq og'zaki ijodi, turli davrlarga xos bo'lgan jargon va slenglarni ham o'rganish zarur. Aks holda, o'rganilgan til nazariy bilimlar darajasida qolib ketishi va haqiqiy muloqotda to'siqlarga olib kelishi mumkin.

Darsliklarda odatda tilning rasmiy, adabiy qoidalari ko'proq o'rin oladi, biroq hayotiy nutq amaliyotida bevosita muomala uchun kerak bo'ladigan unsurlar yetarlicha yoritilmaydi. Shu boisdan ham tilni o'rganishda qo'shimcha usullardan foydalanish muhim hisoblanadi. Masalan, til muhitiga kirish maqsadida o'sha tilda so'zlashuvchi mamlakatga borib tajriba orttirish, til egasi bo'lgan insonlar bilan jonli suhbatlar qurish, badiiy adabiyotlarni o'qish, xorijiy musiqalarni tinglash, radio va podkastlardan foydalanish til o'zlashtirish jarayonini ancha samarali qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, o'rganilayotgan tildagi kino va seriallarni tomosha qilish ham eng qulay va samarali usullardan biri sanaladi. Chunki ular nafaqat so'z boyligini boyitadi, balki turli nutq ohanglari, real hayotiy vaziyatlarda ishlatiladigan iboralar, muloqot madaniyatini ham singdiradi. Shuningdek, filmlar orqali o'quvchilar o'zini tabiiy muhitda his qiladi, turli lahjalarni farqlashni o'rganadi va tilni tezroq o'zlashtiradi.

Filmlar va seriallar chet tili ta'limida qo'shimcha metod sifatida o'ta samarali vosita hisoblanadi. Ular o'quvchilarga tilni kundalik hayotiy vaziyatlarda qanday ishlatilishini amalda namoyish etadi. O'quvchilar darsliklarda kam uchraydigan, lekin og'zaki muloqotda tez-tez ishlatiladigan so'z va iboralarni tezroq o'zlashtira oladi. Bunday yondashuv ularning real muloqotga tayyorlanishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. [1]

Shuningdek, filmlar tilning fonetik xususiyatlarini anglash, tinglab tushunish va talaffuz ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda samarali hisoblanadi. Aktyorlarning turlicha talaffuzi, nutq tezligi va intonatsiyasi o'quvchini haqiqiy til muhitiga yaqinlashtiradi. Buning natijasida o'quvchi so'zlarni eshitib, ularning to'g'ri talaffuzini o'zlashtiradi hamda asta-sekin real nutqda qo'llay boshlaydi.

Bundan tashqari, til o'rganish jarayonida filmlar va seriallar o'quvchiga o'sha xalqning turmush tarzi, urf-odatlari va qadriyatlarini o'rganish imkoniyatini beradi. Demak, kino mahsulotlari nafaqat lingvistik ko'nikmalarni, balki madaniy kompetensiyani ham rivojlantiradi. Natijada tilni o'rganish jarayoni yanada qiziqarli, mazmunli va samarali bo'lib boradi.

Har bir inson o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan individual shaxsdir va ma'lumotlarni qabul qilish jarayoni ham shunga qarab farqlanadi. Kimdir eshitish orqali

tezroq o'rganadi, boshqasi esa kitob o'qish yoki matn bilan ishlash orqali bilim oladi. Psixologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, inson bir vaqtning o'zida ham ko'rib, ham eshitgan ma'lumotni ancha samarali eslab qoladi. Shu bois, chet tilini o'rganishda filmlar tomosha qilish juda foydali usullardan biri hisoblanadi. Film va seriallar jarayonida o'quvchi yangi so'zlar, iboralar va idiomatik ifodalar bilan tanishadi, ularni eslab qolish imkoniyati esa yuqori bo'ladi.

Amaliyot shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'rganuvchi o'ziga yoqqan biror videoni tanlab, uni bir hafta davomida muntazam tinglasa va ko'rsa, yanada yuqori natijaga erishadi. Eng asosiysi, videoni tomosha qilish bilan cheklanmay, undagi notiqlarning so'zlarini ohang va talaffuz bilan birgalikda qayta-qayta takrorlash talab etiladi. Shu tariqa o'rganuvchilar tilni tezroq tushuna boshlaydilar, nutqi esa yanada ravonlashadi. Mazkur metod ko'plab tajribalar orqali sinovdan o'tgan bo'lib, samaradorligi isbotlangan. Shu sababli, chet tilini o'rganishda Shadowing texnikasi nafaqat samarali, balki motivatsion jihatdan ham o'quvchiga katta yordam beradi.[2]

Xulosa qilib aytganda, xorijiy tilni o'rganishda filmlar va seriallar samarali, qiziqarli va qulay usullardan biridir. Ushbu usul yordamida o'quvchi so'z boyligini kengaytiradi, tinglab tushunish va talaffuz ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, til egalarining madaniyati bilan tanishadi. Shunday qilib, kino mahsulotlaridan foydalanish til o'rganish jarayonini samarali tashkil etishda muhim vosita hisoblanadi.

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METHODS OF LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the modern development of the methodology of learning and teaching English. The article analyzes how traditional and modern teaching methods, including mobile applications, online platforms and linguistic technologies, help make the learning process more effective and interactive. Recent innovations and reforms in English language teaching in the context of Uzbekistan, including programs to strengthen the English language in the education system and teacher training, are reviewed. The article also presents the main difficulties in learning English, including language complexity, pronunciation and vocabulary learning problems, and proposed solutions to overcome them.

In general, the article shows how innovations and innovative approaches in learning and teaching English have a positive impact on the educational process, and provides effective ways of learning English in the future.

Keywords: methods; interactive; young generation; education systems of Uzbekistan; innovations; culture; English vocabulary.

English is widely spoken among English-speaking countries and nations throughout the world. For this reason, it belongs to the group of international languages of the planet. It is also the main part of several important specialties, such as international relations, administration, and scientific research, and occupies a high position on several political levels. It is also worth emphasizing that the "Renaissance period" that took place on a global scale greatly contributed to the development of not only technologies, art, music, and astronomy, but also languages and their methods. Nowadays "Teaching methods" are a crucial part of efficient education.

Grammar-based: In this method, the main focus is on grammatical rules, syntax, morphology, and other language structures in language learning. Students are introduced to new grammar rules, sentence structure, and correct word usage. **Translation and Interpretation:** Students are given an understanding of the process of learning a new language by translating from their native language into the new language. Translation in this way often helps in getting acquainted with new words and sentences. **The teacher's main role:** In the traditional method, the teacher is the main leader of the educational process and guides the students in acquiring knowledge. The teacher explains grammar rules and concepts and ensures students learn correct pronunciation and grammar.

Lack of technique: In this method, students learn the language through grammar rules and written exercises instead of learning the language naturally. Aspects such as development of speech, and improvement of speaking skills can be of secondary importance. **Advantages of the traditional method:** There is a complete system for teaching grammar and understanding language structure, and learn the basics of grammar quickly: Students learn the language by mastering grammar rules and translating texts.

Disadvantages Learners mostly learn language based on written and grammatical rules, which does not develop the ability to use it in real-life speech and communication, **passive teaching method:** When the teacher does the main activity, students listen more passively and may be limited in practice.

The government of Uzbekistan has adopted the English language as an integral part of the state education system. In 2018, 1 "New English language teacher training program" was launched. Through this program, the methodological skills of English language teachers are being improved. With the help of new educational programs and approaches, courses and trainings aimed at improving teachers and further strengthening their knowledge of the English language are being organized.

In all general education schools of Uzbekistan, separate hours are allocated for learning English. Since 2019, English has been introduced as a compulsory subject from the 6th grade. This decision is intended to increase the demand for the English language in the education system and prepare the young generation for integration with the global world.

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THE IMPACT OF GAMIFICATION ON YOUNG LEARNERS' MOTIVATION IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. This article examines how gamification influences motivation among young learners in English language classes. Drawing on recent empirical studies and theoretical frameworks-especially Self-Determination Theory, Flow Theory, and Behaviourist principles-it investigates which game elements (e.g., rewards, points, leaderboards, feedback, challenge) are most effective for boosting intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The findings show that when properly designed and implemented, gamification increases engagement, attention span, confidence, and willingness to participate, particularly in vocabulary, grammar, speaking, and listening tasks. However, challenges include teacher training, resource constraints, and risks of overreliance on extrinsic rewards. Recommendations are offered for designing balanced gamified experiences that support long-term motivation and language proficiency.

Keywords: gamification; young learners; English classes; motivational theory; educational technology; engagement

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается влияние геймификации на мотивацию учащихся младшего возраста на занятиях по английскому языку. Опираясь на недавние эмпирические исследования и теоретические подходы, в частности, теорию самодетерминации, теорию потока и принципы бихевиоризма, авторы исследуют, какие игровые элементы (например, награды, баллы, таблицы лидеров, обратная связь, задачи) наиболее эффективны для повышения внутренней и внешней мотивации. Результаты показывают, что при правильном проектировании и внедрении геймификация повышает вовлеченность, концентрацию внимания, уверенность в себе и готовность к участию, особенно в заданиях по лексике, грамматике, говорению и аудированию. Однако существуют и другие сложности, включая подготовку учителей, ограниченность ресурсов и риск чрезмерной зависимости от внешних вознаграждений. Предлагаются рекомендации по разработке сбалансированного игрового опыта, способствующего долгосрочной мотивации и овладению языком.

Ключевые слова: геймификация; учащиеся младшего возраста; занятия по английскому языку; теория мотивации; образовательные технологии; вовлеченность

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz tili darslarida yosh o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. So'nggi empirik tadqiqotlar va nazariy asoslarga, xususan, o'z-o'zini aniqlash nazariyasi, oqim nazariyasi va xulq-atvor tamoyillariga tayanib, qaysi o'yin elementlari (masalan, mukofotlar, ballar, yetakchilar jadvali, fikr-mulohazalar, chaqiruvlar) ichki va tashqi motivatsiyani oshirish uchun eng samarali ekanligini o'rganadi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, agar to'g'ri ishlab chiqilgan va amalga oshirilsa, o'yinlashtirish faollikni, diqqatni jamlashni, ishonchni va ishtirok etish istagini oshiradi, ayniqsa lug'at, grammatika, nutq va tinglash vazifalarida. Biroq, qiyinchiliklar o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, resurslarning cheklanganligi va tashqi mukofotlarga haddan tashqari ishonish xavfini o'z ichiga oladi. Uzoq muddatli motivatsiya va tilni bilishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan muvozanatli o'yin tajribasini yaratish bo'yicha tavsiyalar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'yinlashtirish; yosh o'quvchilar; Ingliz tili darslari; motivatsion nazariya; ta'lim texnologiyasi; jalb qilish

In recent years, educators and researchers have increasingly turned to gamification-the integration of game-like elements into non-game contexts-to enhance student motivation

and engagement. Young learners, typically aged between 5 and 12, are considered especially receptive to playful and interactive learning and thus are ideal candidates for gamification in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) or English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms. Motivation is widely recognized as a critical factor in successful language acquisition. Low motivation often leads to reduced classroom participation, anxiety, and higher dropout rates, especially among young learners. Integrating gamified strategies offers a promising way to address these challenges by making learning enjoyable, interactive, and responsive to learners' psychological needs of competence, autonomy, and relatedness.

Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000) posits that three basic psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—must be met for intrinsic motivation to flourish. In gamified English classes: Autonomy is supported when learners have choices (which tasks, or how to earn points). Competence arises through clear, scaffolded challenges and feedback. Relatedness comes from social game elements like team challenges, leaderboards, or peer comparison.

Flow Theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990) argues that motivation and deep engagement arise when tasks are balanced in difficulty (not too hard, not too easy), when clear goals are present, and when learners receive immediate feedback. Gamified systems often provide these conditions (e.g., levels of difficulty, visible progress bars).

A systematic literature review on gamification in ELT for children aged 5-12 found that tools like Kahoot! and Quizizz improved grammar acquisition and boosted motivation and engagement. journals.researchsynergypress.com

A case study with fifth-grade students (age 10-11) integrating game elements (rewards, challenge, tracking progress) showed measurable increases in both motivation and proficiency after intervention. mjsshonline.com

In another study, the use of a Game-Based Student Response (GBSR) system among eleventh-graders raised intrinsic motivation (through autonomy, competence, and relatedness) and extrinsic motivation (via reward and goal endorsement). jurnalnasional2.ump.ac.id

A study comparing gamified vs. non-gamified instruction on Moodle found that experiential rewards (badges, leaderboards) significantly increased learner motivation and engagement in EFL learners. journal2.uad.ac.id

Research on gamified formative assessment (using Quizizz) demonstrated that assessments with game-features led to not only higher engagement but also better accuracy and retention. SpringerLink

Key Game Elements and Their Motivational Effects

Based on the theoretical and empirical evidence, these are the most impactful game elements for young learners in English classes:

Game Element	Motivational Benefit	Practical Implementation
Rewards / Badges / Points	Boosts extrinsic motivation; promotes goal orientation. Useful for beginners.	Use badges for completing vocabulary sets; points for participation.
Leaderboard Competition	/ Enhances relatedness and excitement; social comparison can motivate.	Friendly team contests; rotating leaderboards to keep fairness.
Challenges Levels	& Helps in maintaining flow; fosters a sense of competence.	Tiered grammar or reading challenges; increasing difficulty.
Immediate Feedback	Prevents confusion; reinforces correct usage; helps mistakes to be corrected quickly.	Quiz tools, interactive games with instant correction.

Game Element	Motivational Benefit	Practical Implementation
Choice Autonomy	& Encourages intrinsic motivation; learners feel ownership.	Let students choose which games / activities; optional bonus tasks.
Narrative Storytelling	/ Makes learning meaningful; increases engagement.	Assign story-based tasks; embed English learning within adventures.

While gamification has strong potential, there are several challenges:

Overreliance on extrinsic rewards can undermine intrinsic motivation over time. If students do tasks only for points, not for learning, the deeper learning suffers.

Resource limitations: Access to technology, internet, teacher training, and infrastructure can limit what is feasible.

Design issues: Poorly designed gamified tasks (too easy, too repetitive, or irrelevant) can bore rather than motivate.

Equity concerns: Not all learners respond equally to competition or public leaderboards. Some may feel discouraged.

Design Recommendations for English Classes

To maximize the motivational impact of gamification for young learners, English teachers should:

Blend extrinsic and intrinsic motivators: Start with rewards, but gradually shift toward tasks that foster internal satisfaction (e.g., achievement, curiosity).

Align games with learning objectives: Game elements must support, not distract from, language goals (vocabulary, grammar, speaking, listening).

Ensure scaffolding and progression: Learners should build skills gradually, with increasing challenges and support.

Provide regular, immediate feedback: Correction and praise should be timely to reinforce learning.

Foster social interaction: Include team games, peer challenges, or collaborative tasks to build relatedness and community.

Be mindful of fairness and transparency: Make sure competition is friendly, and all students have opportunities to succeed.

More longitudinal studies are needed: How does gamification affect motivation and learning over terms/years rather than weeks?

Research in diverse educational contexts (rural vs. urban, low-resource settings) to see how local factors (technology, culture) moderate effects.

Exploring which elements best support different skills (speaking vs. listening vs. writing), and whether gamification works differently for various age bands within “young learners”.

Investigating potential negative effects: burnout, competition stress, or dependency on rewards.

Gamification offers a compelling pathway for enhancing young learners’ motivation in English classes. When well-designed-with game elements that satisfy autonomy, competence, and relatedness-gamification increases engagement, confidence, and achievement. Yet, it must be used thoughtfully, balancing extrinsic rewards with intrinsic satisfaction, accounting for resource constraints, equity, and alignment with learning goals. For English teachers aiming to motivate young learners, gamification is a powerful tool-but like any tool, its effectiveness depends on how it is used.

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ZAMONAVIY TA’LIM TIZIMIDA O’QITUVCHI FAOLIYATINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI HAL ETISH STRATEGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy ta’lim tizimida o‘qituvchi faoliyatining dolzarb muammolari, ularning yuzaga kelish sabablari hamda samarali yechim strategiyalari tahlil etilgan. Ta’lim jarayonida o‘qituvchi rolining o‘zgarishi, innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlarning ahamiyati va pedagogik mahoratni rivojlantirish yo‘llari ilmiy asosda yoritilgan. Shuningdek, raqamli ta’lim muhitida o‘qituvchi kompetensiyasini oshirish bo‘yicha amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: zamonaviy ta’lim, o‘qituvchi faoliyati, innovatsiya, pedagogik innovatsiyalar, malaka oshirish, mentorlik tizimi, pedagogik kompetensiya, raqamli texnologiya, ta’lim sifati.

Bugungi kunda ta’lim tizimi jamiyat taraqqiyotining eng muhim omillaridan biri sifatida inson kapitalini shakllantirish, intellektual salohiyatni rivojlantirish va raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash jarayonida hal qiluvchi ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Shu sababli zamonaviy ta’lim tizimida o‘qituvchi shaxsiga, uning kasbiy mahorati, pedagogik yondashuvi va innovatsion fikrlash darajasiga alohida e’tibor qaratilmoqda. Chunki ta’lim jarayonining sifatini belgilovchi asosiy omil - bu o‘qituvchidir. U nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki o‘quvchining tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi, axloqiy fazilatlarini va ijtimoiy faolligini shakllantiruvchi yetakchidir.

Zamonaviy o‘qituvchining faoliyati murakkab, ko‘p qirrali va yuqori mas’uliyat talab qiluvchi jarayon bo‘lib, u nafaqat an’anaviy bilim berish bilan, balki o‘quvchining mustaqil fikrlashini, ijodkorligini, tanqidiy yondashuvini rivojlantirish bilan ham chambarchas bog‘liqdir. Hozirgi davrda ta’lim tizimi jadal sur’atlar bilan raqamlashtirilmoqda, yangi texnologiyalar, innovatsion metodlar va pedagogik yondashuvlar tatbiq etilmoqda. Bu esa o‘qituvchidan zamon talablariga mos ravishda yangilanish, uzluksiz o‘rganish va o‘z ustida ishlashni taqozo etadi.

Ammo amaliyot shuni ko‘rsatmoqdaki, o‘qituvchi faoliyatida bir qator dolzarb muammolar saqlanib qolmoqda. Jumladan, ta’lim jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalarni samarali qo‘llashdagi qiyinchiliklar, raqamli savodxonlik darajasining yetarli emasligi, metodik ta’minotning sustligi, o‘quvchilar motivatsiyasining pasayishi, shuningdek, ijtimoiy-

iqtisodiy omillarning o'qituvchi faoliyatiga salbiy ta'siri kabi masalalar dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Shu bois, zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchining roli, funksiyasi va mas'uliyati tubdan o'zgarib bormoqda. Endilikda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarga tayyor bilimlarni beruvchi emas, balki ularni o'z bilimini mustaqil ravishda izlab topishga, tahlil qilishga, amaliyotda qo'llashga yo'naltiruvchi fasilitator sifatida maydonga chiqmoqda.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida ta'lim sohasida olib borilayotgan islohotlar ham aynan o'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatini modernizatsiya qilish, pedagogik jarayonni innovatsion asosda tashkil etish, ta'lim sifatini xalqaro mezonlarga moslashtirishga qaratilgan. Bu borada o'qituvchining kasbiy kompetensiyasini oshirish, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish, ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganish va milliy ta'lim amaliyotiga tatbiq etish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuningdek, ta'limda insonparvarlik, shaxsga yo'naltirilganlik, kreativlik, axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalarni samarali qo'llash kabi tamoyillarni hayotga tatbiq etish zamonaviy pedagogning asosiy vazifasiga aylanmoqda.

Shu jihatdan qaraganda, o'qituvchi faoliyatidagi muammolarni aniqlash, ularning sabablarini tahlil qilish hamda samarali hal etish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish nafaqat pedagogika fani, balki butun ta'lim tizimi rivoji uchun dolzarb vazifa sanaladi. Chunki zamonaviy ta'lim sifatini oshirish, yosh avlodni barkamol shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash bevosita o'qituvchining malakasi, ijodkorligi va yangilikka ochiqligiga bog'liqdir. Shu sababli, o'qituvchi faoliyatini har tomonlama takomillashtirish, ularni zamonaviy bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan qurollantirish, kasbiy o'sish uchun zarur sharoit yaratish hozirgi davrning eng muhim strategik masalalaridan biridir.

Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi faoliyati murakkab, ko'p yo'nalishli hamda ijtimoiy jihatdan nihoyatda mas'uliyatli soha hisoblanadi [1,22-b]. O'qituvchi nafaqat dars jarayonining tashkilotchisi, balki o'quvchining tafakkurini shakllantiruvchi, uning ijodiy salohiyatini yuzaga chiqaruvchi va shaxs sifatida kamol topishiga yo'naltiruvchi rahbar sifatida maydonga chiqadi [1,45-b]. Shu boisdan o'qituvchi faoliyati doimiy o'zgarish, yangilanish va yangicha yondashuvni talab qiladi. Ammo zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchi faoliyatining samaradorligiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan bir qator dolzarb muammolar mavjud bo'lib, ularni ilmiy tahlil qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Eng avvalo, o'qituvchilarning pedagogik innovatsiyalarni qabul qilish va ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etishdagi sustligi masalasini ko'rsatish mumkin. Hali ham ko'plab o'qituvchilar an'anaviy o'qitish metodlariga tayanib, yangi pedagogik yondashuvlardan foydalanishga ehtiyotkorlik bilan qaraydilar. [6,37-b]. Bu holat ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchining mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirish, ijodkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash imkoniyatlarini cheklab qo'yadi. Innovatsion metodlarni qo'llash, interaktiv yondashuvlar, loyiha asosida ta'lim, muammoli ta'lim yoki "flipped classroom" (teskari sinf) kabi usullarni amaliyotga kiritish o'qituvchi faoliyatining zamonaviy bosqichida zarurat darajasiga ko'tarilgan. [2, 61-b].

Ikkinchi muammo sifatida raqamli kompetensiya yetishmasligini ta'kidlash lozim. Raqamli asrda o'qituvchi axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalarni chuqur bilishi, turli ta'lim platformalari, onlayn resurslar, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi dasturlar bilan ishlay olishi zarur. Ammo ko'plab pedagoglar hali ham texnologik vositalardan to'liq foydalana olmayapti yoki ularni faqat ma'ruza jarayonini osonlashtiruvchi vosita sifatida ko'radi. Aslida esa raqamli ta'lim muhitida o'qituvchi nafaqat texnik vositalarni bilishi, balki ularni didaktik maqsadlarga mos ravishda qo'llay olishi ham zarur. Shu ma'noda, o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli savodxonlikni oshirishga qaratilgan maxsus malaka oshirish kurslari va o'quv dasturlari ishlab chiqish dolzarb ehtiyoj hisoblanadi.

Shuningdek, o'qituvchining kasbiy rivojlanish tizimi va metodik qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarining yetarli emasligi ham muhim muammolardan biridir. O'qituvchilar o'z faoliyati davomida muntazam o'rganish, tajriba almashish va o'z ustida ishlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak. Afsuski, ayrim hollarda malaka oshirish kurslari faqat nazariy yo'nalishda tashkil etilib, amaliy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga yetarlicha e'tibor qaratilmaydi. Natijada, o'qituvchilar o'z dars jarayoniga zamonaviy metodlarni tatbiq etishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Shu bois, o'qituvchilar o'rtasida mentorlik tizimini yo'lga qo'yish, tajribali pedagoglar tomonidan yosh mutaxassislariga amaliy yordam ko'rsatish, o'zaro tajriba almashish muhitini yaratish muhim strategik yo'nalishlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Bundan tashqari, o'qituvchining mehnat faoliyatiga ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy omillar ham katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Pedagogning ijtimoiy mavqei, moddiy ta'minoti va kasbiy motivatsiyasi uning faoliyat sifati bilan bevosita bog'liq. Rag'batlantirish tizimi, ijtimoiy himoya mexanizmlari, o'qituvchining mehnatini qadrlash darajasi past bo'lsa, bu ularning kasbiy faolligini susaytiradi. Shu sababli, ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarning moddiy rag'batini oshirish, kasbiy o'sish uchun qulay sharoit yaratish, ularning tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash zarurdir.

Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi faqat bilim manbai emas, balki o'quvchining o'rganish jarayonini boshqaruvchi va yo'naltiruvchi shaxsga aylanmoqda. Buning uchun o'qituvchi o'z faoliyatida refleksiya madaniyatini shakllantirishi lozim. [2,112-b]. Ya'ni, har bir dars jarayonini tahlil qilib, o'zining kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlash, o'quvchi bilan muloqotni tahlil qilish, o'z ustida muntazam ishlash o'qituvchining kasbiy o'sishida muhim o'rin tutadi. Bunday yondashuv o'qituvchini nafaqat tajriba orttirishga, balki o'zining innovatsion salohiyatini rivojlantirishga ham undaydi.

Shu bilan birga, o'quvchilarda ta'limga nisbatan qiziqish va motivatsiyani oshirish ham o'qituvchi faoliyatining muhim jihatlaridan biridir. O'qituvchi darsni faqat bilim berish jarayoni sifatida emas, balki ijodiy, interaktiv va hamkorlikda o'rganish muhitini yaratish vositasi sifatida tashkil etishi kerak. Darsda muammoli vaziyatlardan foydalanish, o'quvchilarni mustaqil izlanishga yo'naltirish, o'yinli va loyiha asosidagi o'qitish metodlarini tatbiq etish o'quvchilarning ta'limga bo'lgan ijobiy munosabatini kuchaytiradi.

Umuman olganda, o'qituvchi faoliyatidagi dolzarb muammolarni hal etishning eng samarali yo'li - bu ta'lim tizimiga kompleks yondashuvni joriy etishdir. O'qituvchining raqamli, metodik, kommunikativ va refleksiv kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni ta'lim amaliyotiga uyg'unlashtirish, shuningdek, pedagogik jarayonni insonparvarlik va kreativlik tamoyillari asosida tashkil etish orqali zamonaviy o'qituvchi shaxsini shakllantirish mumkin. Ana shundagina ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligi ortadi, o'qituvchining kasbiy obro'si mustahkamlanadi hamda ta'lim sifati xalqaro mezonlarga mos darajada rivojlanadi.

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi o'qituvchidan yuqori darajadagi kasbiy kompetensiya, kreativ yondashuv va raqamli savodxonlikni talab etadi. O'qituvchilar faoliyatidagi dolzarb muammolarni hal etish innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish, uzluksiz malaka oshirish, mentorlik tizimini kuchaytirish va motivatsion mexanizmlarni qo'llash orqali amalga oshiriladi. Natijada, ta'lim jarayonining sifat ko'rsatkichlari oshadi, o'quvchi shaxsining har tomonlama rivojlanishi uchun qulay muhit yaratiladi.

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ЖАНР ФЭНТЕЗИ НА ВНЕКЛАССНЫХ УРОКАХ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В ШКОЛЬНОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются дидактические и воспитательные возможности жанра фэнтези при организации внеклассных занятий по литературе. Раскрываются особенности восприятия учащимися произведений фэнтези, обозначаются пути интеграции данного жанра в систему литературного образования. Автор предлагает формы и методы работы с произведениями фэнтези, направленные на развитие читательской мотивации, воображения, творческого и критического мышления школьников. Особое внимание уделяется проектным и квест-технологиям, позволяющим расширить границы традиционного урока и повысить интерес обучающихся к чтению.

Ключевые слова: фэнтези, внеклассное чтение, школьная литература, читательская мотивация, проектная деятельность, квест-технологии, творческое мышление.

Введение. Современная школьная практика требует обновления подходов к литературному образованию. Одним из эффективных путей является включение во внеклассную деятельность современных жанров массовой литературы, в частности фэнтези, в внеклассную работу старшей школы. Этот жанр, сочетающий мифологические и реалистические начала, привлекателен для подростков, так как позволяет им искать ответы на экзистенциальные вопросы, моделировать собственный идеальный мир, а также осмысливать нравственные проблемы через художественный вымысел.

Введение жанра фэнтези во внеклассную работу способствует развитию эмоционально-ценностного отношения к чтению и литературе, повышает мотивацию школьников, стимулирует самостоятельную читательскую и творческую активность.

Теоретические и методологические основы жанра фэнтези. Жанр фэнтези сформировался в XX веке на стыке мифологической, сказочной и героико-эпической традиций. Его родоначальниками считаются Дж. Р. Р. Толкин [1], К. С. Льюис [2], позднее – Дж. К. Роулинг [3]. В русской литературе фэнтези активно развивается с 1990-х годов в творчестве Н. Перумова [8], М. Семёновой [4], С. Лукьяненко [5], О. Громыко [6] и др.

Обсуждение и результат. Сегодня фэнтези стало неотъемлемой частью не только литературного, но и художественного пространства в целом: его мотивы и образы активно используются в кино, живописи, компьютерных играх, музыкальных и театральных формах искусства. Несмотря на то, что жанр существует уже более века, он продолжает оставаться динамично развивающимся направлением, корнями

уходящим в мир средневековых легенд, эпических сказаний и мифологических традиций.

Фэнтези (от англ. *fantasy* – «фантазия») – вид фантастической литературы, основанный на использовании мифологических и сказочных мотивов [9]. В современном виде сформировался в начале XX века. Огромное влияние на формирование современного облика фэнтези оказал Джон Рональд Руэл Толкин, за что иногда именуется как Отец фэнтези.

Художественный мир фэнтези строится на основе вымышленных пространств, магии, борьбы добра и зла, образа героя-избранного. Однако в основе сюжетов лежат универсальные нравственные конфликты – выбор, верность, мужество, самопожертвование. Именно эти ценности делают жанр педагогически значимым в работе с подростками. Если говорить о воспитательном потенциале фэнтези в школьной практике, то на наш взгляд, фэнтези способствует формированию духовно-нравственных ориентиров, развивает воображение и эстетическое восприятие, стимулирует интерес к чтению.

На внеклассных занятиях данный жанр помогает:

- воспитывать гуманистическое мировоззрение через метафорические образы и символы;
- развивать эмпатию и умение сопереживать героям;
- актуализировать темы дружбы, выбора, ответственности;
- формировать самостоятельную позицию читателя;
- создавать условия для творческой самореализации обучающихся.

Мы рассматриваем формы и методы внеклассной работы по теме «Фэнтези». Внеклассные занятия по литературе предоставляют широкие возможности для интеграции жанра фэнтези в игровую, исследовательскую и творческую деятельность учащихся. Наиболее эффективными формами работы являются (см. табл. 1):

Таблица 1.

Формы внеклассных занятий

Форма	Пример темы	Методы
Литературная игра	«Путешествие в мир Средиземья»	Ролевое моделирование, квиз
Проект	«Создаем свой мир фантазии»	Коллективный сторителлинг, развитие креативности Canva, Padlet
Викторина	«Фэнтези» сказка для взрослых»	формирование аргументированной речи, дебаты, эссе
Клубная встреча	«Толкин и его наследники»	расширение литературного кругозора презентации, видеопроекты
Квест	«По следам Хогвартса»	развитие критического мышления и командной работы QR-коды, Google Forms
Читательская конференция	«Мир фэнтези глазами подростка»	Доклады, мини-исследования
Креативное письмо	«Напиши свое фэнтези»	Цифровые симуляторы, совместное редактирование

Особое место занимают цифровые инструменты, которые необходимо внедрять в образовательный процесс для самостоятельных работ школьников старшей школы (Canva, Genially, LearningApps, Google Sites), позволяющие визуализировать материал, создавать интерактивные задания и портфолио.

Рассмотрим примерный сценарий внеклассного занятия.

Тема: «Фэнтези: сказка XXI века»

Класс: 9-10

Цель: раскрыть особенности жанра фэнтези и его воспитательное значение.

Этапы занятия:

1. Мотивация: интерактивная викторина «Мир фэнтези» (Kahoot).
2. Мини-лекция: краткий обзор жанра и его авторов.
3. Анализ текста: сравнение фрагментов из Толкина и Роулинг.
4. Творческая мастерская: в группах учащиеся создают описание собственного мира фэнтези – название, символику, героев, конфликт.
5. Презентация мини-проектов
6. Рефлексия: облако слов «Фэнтези – это...» (Mentimeter).
5. Педагогические результаты

Таким образом, использование фэнтези во внеклассной работе:

- повышает читательскую мотивацию и культурный интерес школьников;
- развивает воображение, способность к моделированию и анализу;
- формирует коммуникативную и информационно-цифровую компетентности;
- способствует эмоциональной вовлечённости учащихся в литературный процесс;
- создаёт условия для интеграции литературы с медиаобразованием и искусством.

Заключение. Фэнтези как феномен массовой культуры обладает высоким педагогическим потенциалом. Включение произведений данного жанра во внеклассную практику помогает сделать литературное образование современным, личностно-ориентированным и мотивирующим. Привлечение цифровых инструментов, проектных и игровых технологий открывает новые возможности для формирования читательской компетентности и творческого мышления учащихся.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК СРЕДСТВО АКТИВИЗАЦИИ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные образовательные технологии, используемые при обучении русскому языку в старших классах, как средство активизации познавательной деятельности учащихся. Особое внимание уделяется интеграции цифровых инструментов, проектных и интерактивных методов, а также формированию мотивации и критического мышления. Приводятся примеры эффективных технологий – проблемное, проектное, исследовательское, игровое и смешанное обучение, а также использование цифровых сервисов (Canva, Padlet, LearningApps, Google Classroom и др.).

Ключевые слова: современные образовательные технологии, обучение русскому языку, познавательная активность, старшие школьники, цифровая грамотность, интерактивные методы.

Введение. Современный этап развития образования характеризуется активным внедрением инновационных технологий, ориентированных на личностно-деятельностный подход и цифровизацию образовательного процесса. В обучении русскому языку это выражается в переходе от репродуктивных форм усвоения знаний к интерактивным, исследовательским и коммуникативным видам деятельности. Для старших школьников особенно важно создание условий, способствующих развитию самостоятельного мышления, познавательной инициативы и умения применять знания в новых ситуациях.

Теоретические основы и методология. Активизация познавательной деятельности – это процесс стимулирования внутренней мотивации учащихся к изучению предмета, формирование у них познавательного интереса, самостоятельности и рефлексии. По мнению В. В. Давыдова [4], Л. С. Выготского [3], А. Н. Леонтьева [7], познание развивается в деятельности, которая имеет личностный смысл для ученика. Следовательно, современные технологии должны не только передавать знания, но и побуждать к их самостоятельному открытию.

Современные образовательные технологии, по Г. К. Селевко [1] и В. П. Беспалько [5], – это системно организованные способы и методы обучения, направленные на достижение оптимальных образовательных результатов с учетом индивидуальных особенностей учащихся.

Обсуждение и результат. Классификация и характеристика современных технологий обучения русскому языку:

Проблемное обучение. Данный подход активизирует мышление учащихся, побуждает их самостоятельно искать пути решения языковых задач. Например, при изучении темы «Стили речи» можно предложить проблему: почему один и тот же текст может звучать по-разному в разных стилях?

Решая её, ученики проводят языковые наблюдения, формулируют гипотезы и делают выводы, что способствует развитию исследовательских умений, и совершенствованию цифровой грамотности [7].

Проектное и исследовательское обучение. Проектная деятельность (по Е. С. Полат)[2] позволяет интегрировать знания по русскому языку, литературе, истории, культуре. Старшеклассники могут создавать мультимодальные проекты – инфографики, подкасты, мини-видеоролики о нормах современного русского языка или языковых изменениях в цифровой среде.

Игровые и квест-технологии. Игровое моделирование и web-квесты способствуют формированию мотивации и коммуникативной активности. Например,

Web-квест «Знатоки слова» объединяет исследовательские, творческие и языковые задачи, требующие от учащихся анализа текста, поиска информации и создания собственного цифрового продукта[6].

Смешанное и дистанционное обучение. Смешанное обучение сочетает традиционные и электронные формы. Использование платформ Google Classroom, Quizlet, Padlet, LearningApps, Kahoot! позволяет организовать индивидуальные траектории обучения, мгновенную обратную связь и визуализацию прогресса.

Технология критического мышления. Методы «ИНСЕРТ», «Фишбоун», «Шесть шляп мышления» Э. де Боно применяются при анализе текстов различных функциональных стилей. Они помогают учащимся структурировать знания, формулировать аргументы, развивать речевую и логическую культуру.

Говоря о роли цифровых технологий в обучении, нужно отметить, что они влияют положительно на активизацию познавательной деятельности. Цифровые инструменты делают обучение русскому языку более наглядным, интерактивным и лично значимым. Сервисы Canva, Genially, MindMeister, Trello позволяют визуализировать языковые явления и стимулируют творческую активность. Создание инфографик, мемов, видеороликов на основе лингвистических тем повышает вовлечённость старшеклассников и способствует формированию метапредметных компетенций.

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Аннотация: Методы исследования позволяют добывать информацию об изучаемом предмете, анализировать и обрабатывать полученные данные, включают знания науки в систему известных знаний. Изучение педагогической действительности происходит через педагогическое исследование. По мнению автора, его цель – выявление порядка, регулярности в изучаемом процессе, т. е. установление закона или закономерности. Педагогический эксперимент – это научно поставленный опыт в области учебной или воспитательной работы с целью поиска новых, более эффективных способов решения педагогической проблемы.

Ключевые слова: методы исследования, педагогическое научное исследование, педагогический эксперимент, квазиэксперимент.

У каждого изучающего теорию педагогики рано или поздно возникает вопрос: как получены те или иные выводы, можно ли им доверять? Известно, что ход размышлений исследователя, пути, которые привели его к определенным заключениям, решающим образом сказываются на качестве этих заключений и выводов, поэтому познание предмета педагогики в отрыве от способов получения информации о нем не может быть успешным.

Пути, способы познания объективной реальности называют методами исследования.

Они позволяют добывать информацию об изучаемом предмете, анализировать и обрабатывать полученные данные, включают знания науки в систему известных знаний. Уровень развития науки напрямую связан с применяемыми в ней методами. Каждая наука разрабатывает и использует свои собственные методы, отражающие особенности изучаемых явлений. [5, с. 301]

Изучение педагогической действительности происходит через педагогическое исследование. Его цель – выявление порядка, регулярности в изучаемом процессе, т. е. установление закона или закономерности. Строгий научный педагогический эксперимент должен удовлетворять следующим четырем критериям: 1) предполагать внесение в педагогический процесс чего-либо нового, принципиально нового воздействия (изменения) с целью получения определенного результата; 2) обеспечивать условия, позволяющие выделить связи между воздействием и его результатом; 3) включать достаточно полный, документально фиксируемый учет параметров (показателей) начального и конечного состояния педагогического процесса, различие между которыми и определяет результат эксперимента; 4) быть достаточно доказательным, обеспечивать достоверность выводов.

Педагогическое научное исследование – это процесс формирования новых педагогических знаний, вид познавательной деятельности, направленный на открытие объективных закономерностей обучения, воспитания и развития. Различают три уровня педагогических исследований: 1) эмпирический – устанавливаются новые факты в

педагогической науке; 2) теоретический – выдвигает и формулирует основные, общие педагогические закономерности, позволяющие объяснить ранее открытые факты и предсказать их будущее развитие; 3) методологический – на базе эмпирических и теоретических исследований формулируются общие принципы и методы исследования педагогических явлений, построения теории.[5, с. 270]

Научный эксперимент, выполняемый в рамках научного исследования, имеет целью получить тот или иной педагогический эффект впервые, согласно теоретически сформулированной гипотезе; в научном исследовании новое знание является целью эксперимента, выступает в функции цели.

Педагогический эксперимент – это научно поставленный опыт в области учебной или воспитательной работы с целью поиска новых, более эффективных способов решения педагогической проблемы; исследовательская деятельность по изучению причинно-следственных связей в педагогических явлениях, которая предполагает опытное моделирование педагогического явления и условий его протекания; активное воздействие исследователя на педагогическое явление; измерение результатов взаимодействия и педагогического воздействия; неоднократную воспроизводимость педагогических явлений и процессов.[3, с.177]

Если расположить все встречающиеся на практике случаи по степени выполнения критериев научного экспериментирования, то получится ряд, на одном полюсе которого находятся строго научные эксперименты, а на другом – те, в которых не удовлетворяется ни один из критериев (опытничество типа «попробуем, что получится»). Все эксперименты, находящиеся между этими полюсами, представляют собой нестрогие, так называемые квазиэксперименты, в которых не обеспечены достаточно «чистые» условия, отсутствует должный уровень отслеживания показателей и т. д.

Для обозначения квазиэкспериментов в школьной практике употребляется целый ряд терминов: опытное преподавание, опытная проверка, опытное внедрение, опытное сравнение, апробирование (апробация, проба), пробное использование (применение), экспериментальное обучение, опытно-экспериментальная работа, творческое экспериментирование и др. Резких границ между всеми этими понятиями не существует, а задача исследователя (и методических служб) состоит в возможно большем приближении каждого эксперимента к строгому научному уровню.

Рекомендуемые требования к педагогическому экспериментированию всех видов и уровней можно сформулировать так:

- желание и готовность учителя к экспериментальной работе;
- наличие у экспериментатора определенной гипотезы, которая предполагала бы введение в педагогический процесс какого-либо нового элемента для получения определенного результата;
- тщательная разработка вмешательства в педагогический процесс, обеспечение условий наблюдаемости педагогического воздействия и его следствий;
- соблюдение принципа «не навреди»; обеспечение обязательных результатов обучения, предусмотренных учебным планом;
- тщательная фиксация условий и результатов эксперимента;
- научная честность и добросовестность, стремление к достоверности при формулировании выводов;
- взаимопонимание между исследователем и детьми, благожелательное отношение к эксперименту со стороны окружающих: администрации, родителей и детей. [2, с. 185]

Выделяют следующие типы психолого-педагогических исследований.

1. Обзорно-аналитическое исследование. Предполагает подбор и изучение литературы по проблеме. Основная задача – выделить вопросы, на которые ответы уже найдены, а также вопросы, на которые еще предстоит найти ответы.

2. Обзорно-критическое. Оно сродни аналитическому, но носит критический характер.

3. Теоретическое. Включает, кроме обзора и критического анализа литературы, собственные теоретические предложения автора, направленные на решение поставленной проблемы.

4. Эмпирически-описательное. Здесь опытным путем, с использованием определенных методов сбора и анализа фактов добываются и описываются некоторые новые факты, касающиеся малоизученных объектов или явлений.

5. Эмпирически-объяснительное. Объясняет полученные факты, а не только собирает и описывает их.

6. Методическое. Его цель – разработать, обосновать и проверить на практике какую-либо методику.

7. Экспериментальное. В процессе этого исследования проводится эксперимент.[4, с. 120]

В дальнейшем будем понимать под исследованием наиболее распространенное – экспериментальное исследование.

В основе педагогических исследований лежат следующие принципы.

Принцип единства исторического и логического. Педагог-исследователь обязан в процессе решения проблемы соотносить и учитывать то, что уже сделано в истории педагогики, педагогической теории и практике. Игнорирование этого принципа часто приводит к «изобретению давно забытого старого».

Системный подход. Необходимо рассматривать объект исследования как целостную систему.

Личностный подход. Он требует изучения и учета индивидуальных, возрастных особенностей личности, а также природных возможностей и социальных условий, в которых происходит ее развитие.

Деятельностный подход. Исследователь должен учитывать характерные особенности того вида деятельности, который он организует с учащимися и на основе которой осуществляется их обучение, воспитание, развитие.

Принадлежность какого-либо труда или рукописи к науке определяется по признакам характера целеполагания, выделения специального объекта исследования, применения специальных средств познания, соблюдения однозначности терминологии.

В содержании рефлексии исследования по поводу его принадлежности к науке можно выделить характеристики, позволяющие оценить качество педагогического исследования: проблема, тема, актуальность, объект исследования, его предмет, цель, задачи, гипотеза и защищаемые положения, новизна, значение для науки, значение для практики.

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KOLLABORATIV O‘QITISHNING DIFFERENSIAL TA’LIMNI AMALGA OSHIRISHDAGI O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada differensial ta’limni amalga oshirishda hamkorlikda o‘qitishning o‘ziga xos o‘rni hamda hamkorlikda o‘qitishning asosiy maqsadi – talabalarning mustaqil fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish va ijtimoiy tajribalarni rivojlantirish ekanligi haqida fikrlar yuritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, innovatsion jarayon, differensial ta’lim, o‘quv material, optimallashtirish, hamkorlikda o‘qitish, fikr almashish, bilim, o‘nikma, pedagogik imkoniyat.

Dunyoda hamda mamlakatimizda ta’lim barqaror taraqqiyotni ta’minlaydigan asosiy kuch sifatida e’tirof etilib, kompetensiyaviy yondashuvlar asosida ta’lim jarayonini innovatsion tashkil etish, pedagogik diagnostika metodlaridan optimal foydalanish strategiyalari samaradorligini oshirish va usullarini takomillashtirish orqali tahsil oluvchilar uchun ularning hayoti davomida sifatli ta’lim olish imkoniyatini yaratish aloxida dolzarblik kasb etmoqda.

Differensial ta’lim o‘quv jarayoni tashkiliy shakllaridan biri bo‘lib, bunday ta’lim jarayonida o‘quvchilar ma’lum bir xususiyatlariga ko‘ra guruhlariga ajratiladi va shunga ko‘ra o‘quv jarayoni tashkil etiladi. Differentsiatsiya lotin tilidan olingan bo‘lib, “differentia”– farq, tabaqa ma’nolarini anglatadi [3; 110].

Differentsiallashtirish ta’limning asosiy belgilaridan biri bu o‘quvchilarning turli xususiyatlariga ko‘ra hamkorlikda o‘qitishga hamda o‘quv materialini taqdim etishda har bir guruhning ushbu jihatlarini inobatga olgan holda moslashtirish, to‘ldirish yoki optimallashtirishdan iboratdir.

Differensial ta’limni amalga oshirishda yana bir mexanizm – hamkorlikda (kollaborativ) o‘qitishning o‘ziga xos o‘rni bor. Hamkorlikda o‘qitish texnologiyasi mualliflaridan biri bo‘lgan R.Slavinning ta’kidlashicha, o‘quvchilarga topshiriqlarni hamkorlikda bajarish uchun ko‘rsatma berilishi yetarli emas. O‘quvchilar tom ma’nodagi hamkorlik, har bir o‘quvchining qo‘lga kiritgan muvaffaqiyatidan quvonish, bir-biriga sidqidildan yordam berish hissi, qulay ijtimoiy-psixologik muhit vujudga kelishi zarur. Mazkur texnologiyada o‘quvchilarning bilimlarni o‘zlashtirish sifatini aniqlashda ularni bir-biri bilan emas, balki har bir o‘quvchining kundalik natijasi avval qo‘lga kiritilgan natija bilan taqqoslanadi. Shundagina

o'quvchilar o'zining dars davomida erishgan natijasi guruh(komanda)ga foyda keltirishini anglagan holda mas'uliyatni his qilib, ko'proq izlanishga, bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni o'zlashtirishga harakat qiladi. Hamkorlik pedagogikasida esa, o'quvchi o'z o'quv faoliyatining subyekti sifatida qaraladi. Bunda o'qituvchi va o'quvchi pedagogik jarayonning subyektlari sifatida tenglashib, hamkorlik pedagogikasi jarayoni hosil bo'ladi. Ular o'zaro hamkor, hamdo'st, hamijodkor, hamishtirokchi, hamdard, hamboshqaruvchi bo'ladilar. Hamkorlik munosabatlari o'qituvchilar orasida, ma'muriyat bilan o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar tashkilotlari bilan, rahbarlar, ota-onalar, jamoatchilik orasida ham o'rnatiladi [2; 964–965].

Mazkur mexanizm talabalarning birgalikda ishlash orqali yangi bilimlarni o'zlashtirishiga xizmat qiladi. Bu usulda talabalar bir-birining kuchli tomonlaridan foydalanib, birgalikda ona tili fani yuzasidan beriladigan turli xarakter va murakkablikdagi topshiriqlarni bajarishga muvaffaq bo'lishadi. Hamkorlikka asoslangan differensial ta'limda talabalarning ijtimoiy mahoratlari, birgalikda ishlash qobiliyati va muloqot qobiliyati rivojlanadi. Hamkorlikda o'qitish differensial ta'lim jarayonida talabalarning o'zaro hamkorlik va birgalikda ishlash orqali bilim olishlarini rag'batlantiradi, ular o'zaro bilimi, tajribasi va fikrlaridan o'rnatiladigan muloqot va muhokamalar orqali yangi ma'lumotlarni o'zlashtiradilar. Hamkorlikda o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi – talabalarning mustaqil fikrlash, muam-molarni hal qilish va ijtimoiy tajribalarni rivojlantirishdir.

Hamkorlik pedagogikasi turli mamlakatlarda ilg'or pedagoglar ishtirokidarivojlandi. Ma'lumki, ta'lim sifatini boshqarish – ta'lim jarayoni sifatini loyihalash-tirish, unga erishish va qo'llab-quvvatlash hamda uni amalga oshirishni, natijalarini ta'minlashdan iboratdir. Bunda ta'lim sifatini ta'minlashda zamonaviy yondashuvlarining asosiy negizi – turli xil boshqaruv, innovatsiya va axborot texnologiyalarini ta'limga joriy etishda o'z ifodasini topadi [1]. Ma'lumki, hozirgi davrda yoshlarning kasbiga oid bilimlarini hayotda qullay olishlari uchun keng imkoniyat yaratish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu vazifa ta'lim sifatini yuksak darajada ko'tarishni, puxta va bilimli raqobatbardosh mutaxassis tayyor-lashni, boshqacha qilib aytganda, ta'lim va tarbiya tizimida tub sifat o'zgarish-larini sodir etishni talab qiladi. Demak, hamkorlik pedagogikasi asosida tashkil qilingan ta'lim va tarbiya o'quvchi shaxsining “Men”ini yorqinroq namoyish etishga, qobiliyat va iqtidorini anglashga, uni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ijodkorlikka intilish, yangilik yaratish – hamkorlik pedagogikasining kreativlik belgisi bilan chambarchasdir. Ushbu hamkorlik asosida bunyodkorlikka intilish, fikrlar parvozig a keng yo'l ochadi [5].

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HAMKORLIKDA O'QITISHNING AFZALLIKLARI (ONA TILI DARS MISOLIDA)

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada differensial yondashuvlar zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim qismi ekanligi, differensial yondashuvlar o'qitish jarayonida o'qituvchidan talabalar ehtiyojlarini aniqlash va kollaboratsiya birgalikdagi faoliyat jarayoni bilim almashish, o'qitish va kelishuvga erishish mavjudligi bilan ta'riflanishi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ta'lim, differensial yondashuv, kollaborativ o'qitish, tamoyil, hamkorlikda o'qitish, texnologik yondashuv, birgalikda ishlash, tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim.

Bugungi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida har bir talabaning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlari, bilim darajasi va qobiliyatlarini inobatga olish zarurati tobora oshib bormoqda. Har bir talabab yoki o'quvchi o'rganish jarayonida turli tezlik va usullarda muvaffaqiyatga erishadi, shuning uchun "barchaga bir xil" yondashuv ko'pincha yetarli natija bermaydi. Shaxsiy yondashuvlar va o'quv jarayonini moslashtirish o'quvchilarning o'z imkoniyatlarini to'liq ochishiga yordam beradi va ta'lim sifatini oshiradi. Shu ma'noda, differensial yondashuvlar zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim qismi bo'lib, har bir talabaga individual rivojlanish imkoniyatini taqdim etadi.

Differensial yondashuvlar o'qitish jarayonida o'qituvchidan talabalar ehtiyojlarini aniqlash, ularni turli usullar yordamida qo'llab-quvvatlash hamda ularga mos material va topshiriqlarni tanlashni talab qiladi. Ushbu yondashuvning asosiy afzalligi – ta'lim jarayonini shaxsiylashtirish – talabalarda o'qishga nisbatan ijobiy munosabat shakllantiradi va ular orasida mas'uliyat hissini kuchaytiradi [3; 9].

L.S.Vigotskiy o'zining "Ijtimoiy-madaniy nazariyasi"da bugungi kollaborativ o'qitishning asosiy tamoyillarini ishlab chiqqan [9]. Olimning fikricha, inson tafakkuri hamda bilimi ijtimoiy muloqot va hamkorlik orqali rivojlanadi. Hamkorlikda o'qitish talabalarda birga ishlash, fikrlarni muhokama qilish va o'zaro kelishib olish orqali ijtimoiy tajribalarini oshirish, fikrlarini mustaqil ravishda ifodalash hamda o'zlashtirgan bilimini amalda qo'llash, o'zaro muloqot va muhokamalar orqali ma'lumotlarning ma'nosi hamda qo'llanishini chuqurroq tushunish, bir-biriga yordam berish va birga ishlash orqali o'z vazifalariga mas'uliyat bilan yondashish, didaktik muammolarni hal qilish, tanqidiy fikrlash va ijodiy yondashuv qobiliyatlari rivojlantirishda alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

"Kollaboratsiya" (kollaboration) – umumiy manfaatga birga erishish uchun ikki yoki undan ko'proq kishining sherikchiligi – deb tushunilsa [6], "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati"da: umumiy maqsadga erishish uchun ishtirokchilarning g'oya va imkoniyatlarining birlashishi, hamkorlik deb ta'rif beradi [8]. Ba'zi manbalarda esa "Kollaboratsiya" – (hamkorlik) – ikki yoki undan ortiq shaxs yoki guruhning har qanday sohadagi umumiy maqsadlarga erishish uchun birgalikdagi faoliyat jarayoni hisoblanib, unda bilim almashish, o'qitish va kelishuvga erishish (konsensus) [1] mavjudligi bilan ta'riflandi.

Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoniga texnologik yondashuv masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratilishi, texnologik yondashuvning eng asosiy afzalliklari kutiladigan natija-larning oldindan belgilanishi, ana shu natijalarga asoslangan holda, o'quv maqsadining belgilab olinishi, o'z navbatida ta'lim maqsadini o'quv vazifalarga aylanti-rilishi, ta'lim shakli, metod va vositalarini to'g'ri tanlab olinishi, o'qituvchi hamda ta'lim oluvchi faoliyati bosqichlarining alohida-alohida loyihalab olinishini tashkil etadi [4; 216].

Kollaborativ o'qitishning ona tili va uni o'qitish metodikasi fanlarida butun guruh bo'lib, kichik guruhlariga bo'linib, birgalikda mashqlarni bajarish, muhokama va debatlarida

bir mavzu bo'yicha fikrlarini muhokama qilish, loyihalar ustida ishlash, o'zaro o'rganish, fikr almashish kabi turlaridan foydalanish ijobiy samaraga ega.

Hamkorlikda o'qitishning afzalliklari talabalarni faollashtirish, ular orasida o'zaro hurmat va mas'uliyatni o'stirish, muloqot, ijtimoiy tajribalarini oshirish, o'zlashtirgan bilimni amalda qo'llash imkoniyatini oshirish imkoniyatlarida ko'rinadi. O'z navbatida, hamkorlikda o'qitishning faoliyatda ba'zi talabalar ishtirok etmasligi mumkinligi, guruhdagi notenglik (ba'zilar ko'p, ba'zilar oz ishlashi oqibatida), vaqtni noto'g'ri sarflash mumkinligi kabi pedagogik va psixologik nuqsonlari uchrashini ham e'tirof etish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Shunga qaramasdan, hamkorlikda o'qitish tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning muhim mexanizmi sifatida zamonaviy ta'limning muhim qismi bo'lib, talabalarining ijtimoiy, intellektual va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilganligi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Bu usulning muvaffaqiyati o'qituvchining metodik jihatdan to'g'ri yo'l-yo'riqlari va talabalarining faol ishtirokini ta'minlash bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Talabalarining birgalikda ishlash malakalarini oshirish uchun guruh va jamoaviy loyihalar qo'llanilishini rag'batlantirish lozim. Bu ular orasida hamkorlik va o'zaro yordam ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Differensial yondashuvlar orqali har bir talabaga moslashtirilgan ta'lim jarayoni tashkil etish nafaqat ta'lim sifati, balki o'quvchilarning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishiga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu sababli, ushbu yondashuvlarni ta'lim tizimida keng qo'llash va takomillashtirish ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilishning muhim yo'nalishi hisoblanadi.

Xulosa shuki, tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limni amalga oshirish mexanizmlari ona tili-o'qish savodxonligi va uni o'qitish metodikasi fanini o'qitishda talabalarining individual ehtiyojlarini qondirish, ularning qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish va o'quv jarayoniga qiziqishlarini oshirishda muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Ushbu mexanizmlarni amaliyotga tatbiq etish orqali talabalarining ona tilidagi bilim va ko'nikmalarini samarali rivojlantirish, birga ishlash, fikrlarni muhokama qilish va o'zaro kelishib olish orqali ijtimoiy tajribalarini oshirish, o'z fikrlarini mustaqil ravishda ifodalash va o'zlashtirgan bilimni amalda qo'llash tajribalari shakllanadi.

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MUAMMOLI TA'LIM – TALABALARNING TANQIDIY FIKRLASH VA MUAMMOLARNI YECHISHGA ASOSLANGAN PEDAGOGIK USUL

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada muammoli ta'lim bu mantiqiy fikrlash, tahlil qilish, izlanish, umumlashtirish, muammoli vaziyatlar, echim topish, bilishga qiziqish, ehtiyoj, usullar qo'llaniladigan bir yangicha tizim ekanligi, tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning muammoli o'qitish mexanizmi va Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari – o'quvchi faoliyatini faollashtirish va jadallashtirishga asoslanganligi haqida fikrlar yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ta'lim, muammoli ta'lim, ta'lim mazmuni, tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim, muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari, kommunikativ qobiliyat, differensial ta'lim.

Bugungi zamonaviy ta'lim yoshlardan kuchli salohiyatli, raqobatbardosh, maxsus qobiliyatli, zamon bilan hamnafas, maqsadli, ilmiy-texnika taraqqiyot talablariga javob beradigan, mustahkam irodali bo'lishni talab etadi. Bu kabi sifatlarni amalga oshirilishda esa muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Muammoli ta'lim bu mantiqiy fikrlash, tahlil qilish, izlanish, umumlashtirish, muammoli vaziyatlar, echim topish, bilishga qiziqish, ehtiyoj, usullar qo'llaniladigan bir yangicha tizimidir [2; 248].

So'ngi yillarda ta'lim mazmunini samaradorligini oshiruvchi ta'limning bir qator ishonchli interfaol metod va yo'llari izlanmoqda. Hozirgi kun tajribasida muammoli ta'lim deganda mashg'ulotlarda o'qituvchi-pedagoglar tomonidan yaratiladigan muammoli vaziyatlar va ularni yechishga qaratilgan o'quvchilarning faol mustaqil faoliyati tushuniladi. Buning natijasida talabalar kasbiy bilimlarga, ko'nikmalarga ega bo'ladi va fikrlash qobiliyatlari rivojlanadi [4; 144].

Tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning muammoli o'qitish mexanizmi talabalarga muammoni aniqlab, uni yechish uchun yangi bilimlarni izlash, ta'lim jarayonida talabalarining mustaqil fikrlash, tadqiqot va yechim topish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratiladi. Bu usulda talabalar muammoli vaziyatlarga duch kelib, ularni mustaqil yoki guruh bo'lib hal qilish orqali bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'ladilar. Muammoli ta'limning asoschisi **Djon Dyui** hisoblanadi [6]. U XX asr boshida ta'limda faol ta'lim usullarini targ'ib qilgan. Dyuning fikricha, differensial ta'lim jarayonida talabalar faol ishtirok etishi va o'z bilimlarini amaliy tajriba orqali qo'lga kiritishlari kerak bo'ladi.

Muammoli ta'lim – ta'lim jarayonini olib borishda o'quvchilar oldiga yechish uchun muammoni qo'yish orqali muammoli vaziyatni vujudga keltirish va mashg'ulot davomida uning yechimini topish. Muammo o'qituvchi tomonidan yoki o'quvchilar tomonidan qo'yilishi mumkin. Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari – o'quvchi faoliyatini faollashtirish va jadallashtirishga asoslangan [5].

Muammoli ta'limning asosiy turlari sifatida **muammoli topshiriqlar, loyiha asosida o'qitish, tadqiqot va izlanishlarga jalb qilish qayd etiladi [3; 240]. Bunda** talabalarga muammoli savol va vaziyatlar berish, muayyan loyihani bajarish orqali bilim olish, mustaqil ravishda ma'lumot to'plash va tahlil qilish orqali muammolarni yechish ko'nikmalari shakllantiriladi. Muammoli ta'limning mohiyati – talabalar-ning fikrlash, muammolarni aniqlab, ularga yechim topish qobiliyatlarini rivojlan-tirishda korinadi. Bu usulda o'qituvchi talabalarga tayyor yechimlarni bermaydi, balki ularni mustaqil fikrlashga undaydi.

Muammoli ta'limning o'ziga xos **afzalliklari mavjud bo'lib, ulardan** talabalar muammolarni o'zi yechish orqali mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini oshirish, qiziqishlarini uyg'otish, nazariy bilimlarni amalda ijodiy qo'llash, guruhda ishlash orqali ijtimoiy tajribalarini oshirish imkoniyatlarini alohida ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin.

Muammoli ta'limning o'ziga xos qiyinchiliklari sifatida ta'lim jarayoni ancha vaqt olishi, **har bir talabaga moslashtirishning qiyin** kechishi, ya'ni barcha talabalarining bilim

darajasi va qobiliyati turlicha bo'lishi mumkinligi, muammoli ta'lim uchun qo'shimcha materiallar va manbalar, resurslar kerak bo'lishini e'tirof etish kerak bo'ladi.

Muammoli ta'lim ijtimoiy-pedagogik jihatdan quyidagi ahamiyatga ega:

– **ijtimoiy munosabatlarni rivojlantiradi** – talabalar guruhda ishlash orqali ijtimoiy tajriba va mahoratlarni oshiradi;

– **ijtimoiy muammolarni yechishga tayyorlaydi** – talabalar ijtimoiy muammolarni aniqlab, ularga yechim topishga o'rganadi;

– **faol fuqarolik pozitsiyalarini shakllantiradi** – muammolarni yechish orqali talabalar ijtimoiy jarayonlarga faol ishtirok etishga tayyor bo'ladi.

Djon Dyui: “Muammoli ta'lim – bu hayotga tayyorgarlik emas, balki hayoting o'zidir deb differensial ta'lim jarayonida talabalar bilim va ko'nikmalarni amaliy tajriba orqali o'rganishi kerak”ligini ta'kidlasa, **Lev Vigotskiy [6]:** “Muammoli ta'lim talabaning rivojlanish zonasiga ta'sir ko'rsatishi kerak, bu uning differensial ta'limda mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini oshiradi”, deb yozadi [1; 68]. O'z navbatida, **Jan Piaje [7]:** “Muammoli ta'lim talabaning kognitiv rivojlanishiga yordam beradi, chunki ular differensial ta'limda yangi ma'lumotlarni o'zlashtirish va ularni amalda qo'llash orqali o'rganadi”, deb hisoblaydi.

Ma'lum bo'ladiki, tabaqalashtirib o'qitishda muammoli ta'lim talabalarning tanqidiy fikrlash va muammolarni, mustaqil fikrlash, tahlil qilish va muammolarni yechish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga asoslangan pedagogik usuldir. Bu usulda talabalarga muammoli vaziyatlar taqdim etiladi, ularning yechimini topish uchun talabalar o'zlari tadqiqot olib borishlari, yangi bilimlarni o'zlashtirishlari va ijodiy fikrlashlari talab qilinadi.

Muammoli ta'limning asosiy mexanizmlarini quyidagilar tashkil qiladi: **muammoli vaziyatlarni yaratishda** talabalarga tushunishli bo'lmagan, ammo hal qilishi mumkin bo'lgan masalalar taqdim etiladi; **tadqiqot va izlanish jarayonida** talabalar muammolarni yechish uchun o'zlari ma'lumot to'plash, tahlil qilish va farazlarni tekshirishlari kerak bo'ladi; **hamkorlik va muloqot paytida** talabalar birgalikda ishlash, fikrlarni almashish va bir-birining javoblarini baholash orqali o'rganishadi hamda **natijalarni umumlashtirishda** talabalar topgan yechimlarni tahlil qilish va ularning amaliy ahamiyatini baholashlari talab qilinadi.

Tabaqalashtirib o'qitishda muammoli ta'limning asosiy pedagogik ahamiyati: **mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirish** talabalarning muammolarni yechish orqali mustaqil fikrlash va qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatini oshiradi; **ijodiylikni rivojlantirish** yangi yechimlarni izlash va yangi yo'naltirishlarni sintaksislash orqali ijodiylik qobiliyati oshiriladi; **bilimlarni chuqur o'zlashtirish** talabalar o'zlashtirgan bilimlarni amalda qo'llash orqali chuqurroq tushunishga erishtiradi va **kommunikativ qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish asosida** guruhda ishlash va fikrlarni muloqot orqali ifodalash qobiliyati oshiriladi.

Muammoli ta'lim zamonaviy differensial ta'lim jarayonlarida keng qo'llaniladi va talabalarning shaxsiy rivojlanishiga katta hissa qo'shadi.

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TA'LIMDA INTEGRATSIYANING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada pedagogik jarayonda noan'anaviy o'qitish shakli – integratsiyalashgan ta'limning ahamiyati, fanlarning yaqinlashishi va o'zaro aloqa jarayoni haqida fikr-mulohazalar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: individual yondashuv, modernizatsiyalash, integratsiyalash, tabaqalashtirish, integratsiya prinsip, an'anaviy texnologiyalar, pedagogik yechimlar.

Dunyoda integrativ ta'limning rivojlanishi ijtimoiy hamda axborot kommunikatsiya sohalarining o'zaro tizimli aloqadorligi, ilm-fanning istalgan yo'nalishida kuzatilayotgan integrativ jarayonlarning barchasi jamiyatning zamonaviy ta'limni oldiga qo'ygan talablarini qondirishga qaratilgan o'quv-tarbiya jarayonini samarasini ta'minlashning ustuvor strategiyasini belgilaydi [1].

Pedagogik jarayonga integratsiyalashgan holda rivojlanish jarayoni – ilgari bir-biridan farq qiladigan qismlarni bir butunga birlashtirish bilan bog'liq jihatlaridan birini tushunishdir. Bu jarayon allaqachon tuzilgan tizim doirasida ham, yangi tizim doirasida ham amalga oshishi mumkin. Integratsiya jarayonining mohiyati tizimga kiritilgan har bir element ichidagi sifat o'zgarishlaridir.

Bugungi kunga kelib, an'anaviy o'qitish o'rni shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlar egallamoqda. Bu o'rinda noan'anaviy o'qitish shakli – integratsiya-ning ahamiyati yanada oshib boradi, negaki, integrativ ta'limning darajasiga qarab, uning qo'llanilish texnikasiga ko'ra, amalga oshirilgan texnologiyaning istiqbolini belgilash mumkin bo'ladi. Zero, integratsiya yetarlicha namoyon bo'la olgan, turli xarakterli mazmunning singdirilishi natijasida yangi sifatiy holatga o'tishda asosiy omil bo'lib yuzaga chiqqan oluvchi faktor hisoblanadi. Integratsiya chuqur, noan'anaviy ta'lim bilan tavsiflana oluvchi, turfa xarakterdagi katta hajmli o'quv materialining uyg'unlashuvini o'zida namoyon etadi [3].

Hozirgi kunda bir qator o'quv predmetlari uchun umumiy bo'lgan tushunchalar orasidagi aloqalarni o'rnatish psixologik va metodik asos bo'lgan integratsiyalangan darslar tizimini ishlab chiqish va sinovdan o'lkazish lozim. Shu bilan birga predmetlararo aloqalar dars tarkibi darajasida o'rgatilishi va zarur o'qitish vositalari bilan ta'minlanishi kerak. Integratsiyalashgan darslar – interaktiv ta'lim tizimi bo'lib, integrativ bilimlarni chuqurlashtirish va kengaytirish asosida ko'rgazmali mahoratni vujudga keltirish sirlarini o'rganadi. Ko'rgazmali ta'lim tizimi turli xildagi turlar, shakllar, usullar, obyektlar asosida qurilgan [2; 149].

Integratsiya (lotincha *integratio* – tiklash, to'ldirish, *integer* – butun so'zidan) – bu suveren davlatlar o'rtasida tovarlar, xizmatlar, moliya, investitsiya, ishchi kuchi erkin harakatlanadigan iqtisodiy kenglikni tashkil qilish maqsadida birlashish jarayoni: sistema yoki organizmning ayrim qismlari va funksiyalarining o'zaro bog'liqlik holatini hamda

shunday holatga olib boruvchi jarayonni ifodalaydigan tushuncha; fanlarning yaqinlashishi va o'zaro aloqa jarayoni; differentsiatsiya bilan birga kichadi va Ikki va undan ortiq davlatlarning iqtisodiyotini o'zaro muvofiq-lashtirish va birlashtirish [3].

Integratsiya tushunchasi quyidagi ikki xil jarayon sifatida talqin etiladi: birinchidan, tizim, organizmning alohida tabaqalashtirilgan qism va vazifalarning bog'liqlik holatini bildiruvchi tushuncha va shu holatga olib boruvchi jarayon; ikkinchidan, tabaqalashtirish jarayonlari bilan birga amalga oshirilayotgan fanlarni yaqinlashtirish jarayoni [1; 129]. Demak, ta'limdagi integratsiya fanlarning yaqinlashishi va o'zaro aloqa jarayoni; tabaqalashtirish jarayonlari bilan birga amalga oshirilayotgan fanlarni yaqinlashtirish jarayoni tushuniladi.

Jamiyatdagi integratsiya jarayonida insonning integratsiya – alohida element-larni yig'ib, ularni birlashtirish, yaxlit holga keltirish deb tushunish mumkin. Shuningdek, ko'pchilik olim va metodistlar integratsiya muammosining mazmun-mohiyatini aniqlash bo'yicha fikr berganlar. Hozirgi kunda "Integratsiya" tushunchasining aniq ta'rifini metodik adabiyotlarda, bu muammo bo'yicha shug'ullangan olimlar tomonidan bir-biriga yaqin bo'lgan ta'riflarda berilgan. Ta'limni integratsiyalashning asosiy maqsadi boshlang'ich maktabdoyoq tabiat va jamiyat haqida yaxshi tasavvur asoslarini qo'yish va ularning rivojlanishi qonunlariga o'z munosabatini shakllantirishdir. Mana shuning uchun kichik maktab o'quvchisi predmet yoki voqea hodisalarni bir necha tomondan ko'rishi muhim: mantiqiy va emotsional tomondan badiiy asarda hamda ilmiy-ommabop maqolada biolog, so'z ustasi, rassom, musiqachi nuqtai nazaridan va boshqalar. Ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda yashirin aloqadorlik va bog'lanishlarni aniqlay bilish, fanlararo bog'lanish, ya'ni uzviylikni ta'minlash bugungi kunning eng dolzarb masalalaridan biridir. Chunki fanlararo aloqadorlik ta'minlangan holda, darsni tashkil qila olgan o'qituvchi o'quvchilarda o'zining faniga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiribgina qolmasdan, mazkur fanni o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish joizki, integratsiya pedagogik hodisa sifatida maktab fanlarining birligiga yondashuvning yangi bosqichiga aylangan. Turli xil obyektlardagi hodisalarning bir-biriga mos kelishiga imkon beradigan fanlararo aloqalarni amalga oshirish bosqichlaridan ushbu hodisalarni birlashtirishga, yangi yaxlitliklarning yaratilishiga o'tish kerak, ya'ni haqiqiy integratsiya misolida amalga oshiriladi. Demak, zamonaviy maktabda fanlarning integratsiyasi yangi pedagogik yechimlarni faol izlash, o'quvchilarga samarali va asosli ta'sir ko'rsatish uchun pedagogik xodimlarning ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlaridan biri xisoblanadi.

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DARS JARAYONIDA KONTSEPTUAL JADVALLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada ta'lim jarayonini vizuallashtirish, uning mohiyati hamda kontseptual jadval, grafik organayzerlarning turlari, ularni qo'llash tartibi hamda didaktik ahamiyati yoritilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur hodisa yuzasidan taniqli olimlarning pedagogik qarashlari o'z aksini topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik texnologiya, vizuallashtirish, kontseptual jadval, grafik, grafik organayzer, rasm, diagramma, jadval, sxema, video, slayd.

Prezidentimiz Sh.Mirziyoyevning: "Agar mendan sizni nima qiynaydi, deb so'rasangiz, farzandlarimizning ta'limi va tarbiyasi deb javob beraman", deya aytgan e'tiroflari, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan har bir islohot zamirida o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodning kelajagi, mukammal bilim sohiblari bo'lib kamol topishlari va yorqin istiqboli masalasi yotganligini ko'rsatadi [6; 7; 696].

Axborot texnologiyalar asrida bugungi kunda yoshlarimiz shiddat bilan o'rganib borayotgan innovatsion texnologiyalar bilan uqtirib borish o'qituvchilar zimmasiga katta mas'uliyat yuklaydi. Shunday ekan, bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning bilim, salohiyat egasi bo'lishi bilan bir qatorda ta'limga innovatsion yondashish, qolaversa, ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni o'rgangan holda ta'lim sifatini yanada oshirish muhim ahamiyatga molikdir. Bo'lajak o'qituvchining pedagogik faoliyatida o'qituvchilar bilan olib boradigan muloqoti muhim ta'lim-tarbiyaviy ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, o'qituvchilar bilan ta'lim jarayonida yetarli darajada samaraga erishishning asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi [1; 11].

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan ustuvor vazifalardan biri ta'lim sifatini oshirish hamda yangi avlod o'qituvchilarini zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar bilan qurollantirishdin iborat. Boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida o'qitish jarayonini vizuallashtirish, ya'ni bilimlarni tuzilmali va mantiqiy ravishda shakllantirishning innovatsion usullari, xususan, kontseptual jadvallar va grafik organayzerlardan samarali foydalanish dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

A.Shodievning e'tiroficha, vizual vositalar bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari uchun, nafaqat ta'limni samarali tashkil etish, balki o'qituvchilarning kreativ va mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantirishda alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi [10; 8]. Mazkur maqolada ta'lim jarayonida kontseptual jadval hamda grafik organayzerlardan foydalanish kompetentligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish metodikasining samaradorligiga qaratilgan fikrlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kontseptual jadval va grafik organayzerlar mavzuga oid ma'lumotlarni tizim va mantiqiy aloqalar asosida taqdim etishga xizmat qiluvchi vizual vositalardir. Ular o'qituvchilarga murakkab tushunchalarni anglash, muhim ma'lumotlarni aniqlash, umumlashtirish va taqqoslash imkonini beradi. Vizual vositalarning ilmiy asoslari kognitiv psixologik, konstruktiv ta'lim nazariyalari va pedagogik texnologiyalar bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Ta'limda vizual vositalardan foydalanish o'qituvchilarda mantiqiy fikrlash, bilimlarni tizimlashtirish, tahlil qilish, yangicha yondashuvlarni qo'llash kabi kompetentsiyalar shakllanishiga yordam beradi.

Taniqli olim R.E.Mayerning “Kognitiv multimedia ta’lim nazariyasi”ga ko‘ra, vizual vositalar didaktik mavzu mazmunini ma’lumotlarini grafik, rasm, diagramma, jadval, sxema, video, slayd kabi ko‘rinishda taqdim etishda qo‘llanila-digan didaktik vositalardir [3; 44].

Kontseptual jadval va grafik organayzerlar mavzuga oid ma’lumotlarni tizim va mantiqiy aloqalar asosida taqdim etishga xizmat qiluvchi vizual vositalardir. Ular o‘quvchilarga murakkab tushunchalarni anglash, muhim ma’lumotlarni aniqlash, umumlashtirish va taqqoslash imkonini beradi. Vizual vositalarning ilmiy asoslari kognitiv psixologik, konstruktiv ta’lim nazariyalari va pedagogik texnologiyalar bilan chambarchas bog‘liq.

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O‘quvchilari bilimni chuqurlashtirishda bu vositalardan to‘g‘ri foydalanish o‘qituvchi salohiyatiga bog‘liq. Shu nuqtai nazardan, pedagog kadrlarni tayyorlash jarayonida bu o‘qitish qurollaridan samarali foydalanish kompetentligini shakllantirish dolzarb vazifalardan biridir. Vizual vositalardan foydalanish kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasining mazmunini nazariy asos, amaliy va tahliliy ko‘nikmalar majmui tashkil qiladi: nazariy asos kontseptual jadval va grafik organayzerlarning nazariy jihatdan asoslab berilishini nazarda tutadi; amaliyotga yo‘naltirilgan mashg‘ulotlar esa bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarni vizual modellar tuzishga o‘rgatadi hamda tahliliy ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantirish talabalarida ma’lumotlarni tahlil qilish, tizimlash va umumlashtirish usullarini qo‘llash ko‘nikmalarini tarbiyalaydi.

Sanab o‘tilgan metodika asosida, maxsus treninglar, amaliy mashg‘ulotlar, metodik ko‘rsatmalar ishlab chiqildi va joriy etilishi ta’limiy faoliyat jarayonida talabalarida bilimlar tizimli shakllanishi hamda ularni amaliyotda qo‘llash qobiliyati shakllanishiga xizmat qiladi. Kontseptual jadvallar ma’lumotlarni qisqa, ixcham shaklda ko‘rsatish imkonini beradi, bilimlarni tizimga soladi va o‘rganish jarayonini osonlashtiradi. Grafik organayzerlar esa talabalaridagi mavjud turli tarqoq bilimlarni o‘zaro bog‘liqlikda vizual ravishda namoyon qilish orqali murakkab tushunchalarni anglashiga yordam beradi.

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INDIVIDUAL TA’LIM – TA’LIM SHAKLLARINING ENG QADIMIYSI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada guruhlarga ajratib o'qitish, ularning mustaqil ishlarini to'g'ri va maqsadga muvofiq tashkil etish orqali barcha bilim va malakalarini dinamik rivojlanishiga xizmat qilishi va, ayniqsa, individual ta'lim deganda, talabaning shaxsiy qobiliyatlari, qiziqishlari, boshlang'ich bilim darajasi va o'rganish tezligini hisobga olgan holda, uning ta'lim traektoriyasini shaxsiy ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish tushinilish haqida fikrlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy pedagogika, individual ta'lim, pedagogik mexanizm, til mexanizm, tabaqashtirilgan ta'lim, individual qobiliyatlari, pedagogik yondashuv, hamkorlik va muloqot.

O'zbekiston ta'limi tarixida Individual ta'lim shakli keng qo'llanib kelingan. Uning samarasi, ayniqsa, amaliy san'at, hunarmandchilikda ustoz-shogird ta'limi tarzida namoyon bo'lgan. Mashhur xalq ustalari Toshpo'lat Arslonqulov, Usta Shirin Murodov, Qodirjon Xaydarov, Mahmud Usmonov, Hamro Rahimovlar shu tarzda ta'lim olganlar. Individual ta'limda bola ruhiyatining individual xususiyatlarini, fan sohalari va kasb egallashga bo'lgan tabiiy moyilliklarini to'liq e'tiborga olish imkoniyati ta'minlanadi [8].

Individual ta'lim – o'qituvchining o'quvchiga pedagogik ta'sirini amalga oshiruvchi o'quv mashg'ulotlari shakllaridan biri. O'qituvchining o'quvchi bilan sinf jamoasidan tashqarida olib boriladigan faoliyati tushuniladi. Individual ta'lim ta'lim shakllarining eng qadimiysi bo'lib, u qadimgi davr va o'rta asrlarda keng qo'llangan [8].

Differensiyal ta'lim o'quvchilarning individual tarzda, shuningdek, guruhlarga ajratib o'qitish, ularning mustaqil ishlarini to'g'ri va maqsadga muvofiq tashkil etish orqali barcha bilim va malakalarini dinamik rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Bunda o'qituvchi har bir o'quvchining qiziqishi, qobiliyati, layoqatini hisobga olib, mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish orqali dars samaradorligini oshirishiga erishadi [5; 360].

Tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim – bu talabalarning individual qobiliyatlari, qiziqishlari va tayyorgarlik darajasini hisobga olib, ularga moslash-tirilgan ta'lim berish usulidir. Ona tili-o'qish savoxonligi va uni o'qitish metodikasi fanini o'qitishda tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning mexanizmlari va ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etish usullaridan biri sifatida individual ta'lim haqida fikr yuritsak.

Jon Dyui "Ta'lim kelajak hayotga tayyorgarlik emas, balki hayotning o'zi jarayonidir" [7] degan edilar. Individual ta'limning asoschisi ham Jon Dyui hisoblanadi. U XX asrning boshlarida ta'limda talabaning shaxsiy ehtiyojlari va qiziqishlariga alohida e'tibor berishni targ'ib qilgan. Dyuning individual ta'limga oid fikrlari progressiv ta'limning asosini yaratdi, bu esa o'z navbatida individual ta'limning butun dunyo miqyosida rivojlanishiga xizmat qildi.

Individual ta'lim har bir talabaning kuchli va sust tomonlarini aniqlab, ularga moslashtirilgan o'quv materiallari va vazifalarni tayyorlashni nazarda tutadi. Individuallashtirib o'qitish mexanizmini amaliyotda tatbiq etishning ko'p tarqalgan usullari sifatida talabalarni tayyorgarlik darajasiga qarab guruhlarga ajratish hamda har bir talabaga alohida o'quv rejasi tuzish asosida amalga oshiriladi. Bunda nisbatan past o'zlashtirish darajasiga ega bo'lgan talabalarga ona tilining grammatik qoidalarini tushunib yetishlari uchun ularga qo'shimcha mashqlar taklif etish ko'zda tutiladi. Individual ta'lim deganda, talabaning shaxsiy qobiliyatlari, qiziqishlari, boshlang'ich bilim darajasi va o'rganish tezligini hisobga olgan holda, uning ta'lim traektoriyasini shaxsiy ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish tushiniladi. Bu kabi ta'lim jarayonida talabaning faolligi va mustaqilligi oshiriladi, talaba o'z ta'lim traektoriyasining asosiy subyektiga aylanadi.

Manbalarda individual ta'limni amalga oshirishning quyidagi tamoyillari o'zaro farqlanadi: shaxsiy ehtiyojlarga moslashtirish: har bir talabani o'ziga xos qobiliyatlari va ehtiyojlarini hisobga olish; faol o'rganish: talabani o'z bilimni mustaqil ravishda qurishi va izlash faolligini oshirish; ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanish: talabani ijtimoiy va hissiy jihatdan rivojlanishiga yordam berish; tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim: talabalarning bilim darajasiga qarab o'quv materiallarini moslashtirish va texnologiyalardan foydalanish: zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida talabalarga shaxsiy ta'lim yo'llarini taqdim etish.

Individual ta'lim mexanizmlarini amalga oshirishda quyidagi tarkibiy qismlar taqozo qilinadi: shaxsiy o'quv rejalar: har bir talaba uchun uning qobiliyatlari va maqsadiga mos reja tuzish; monitoring va baholash: talabani rivojini muntazam ravishda ko'rib borish va uning natijalarini baholash; pedagogik yondashuvning xilma-xilligi: talabalarning turli o'rganish usullariga mos keladigan pedagogik usullarni qo'llash; texnologiyalarni qo'llash: maxsus dasturlar va platformalar orqali talabalarga shaxsiy ta'lim yo'llarini taqdim etish va hamkorlik va muloqot: talaba, ota-ona va o'qituvchilar o'rtasida doimiy aloqa va hamkorlikni ta'minlash.

Individual ta'lim asosida talabani faolligi, mustaqilligi va ijtimoiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash maqsadi qo'yiladi. Bu ta'limni amalga oshirishda zamonaviy texnologiyalar, tabaqalashtirilgan ta'lim usullari va shaxsiy rejalar keng qo'llaniladi.

Individual ta'lim har bir talabani shaxsiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish, uning ta'limdagi muvaffaqiyatini oshirish va ijtimoiy rivojlanishini ta'minlashda muhim vositadir. Bu ta'lim turlarining har biri o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, pedagogik amaliyotda ularning ahamiyatini inobatga olish ta'lim tizimining samaradorligini oshirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Individual ta'lim turlari va ularning xususiyatlari xususida quyidagi fikrlarni ifodalash mumkin: individual ta'lim dasturining xususiyati shundaki, u asosan turli bilish darajasi va imkoniyatiga ega talabalarga ularning kuchli hamda zaif jihatlari inobatga olinadi, shaxsiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish, uning ta'limdagi muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlash va ijtimoiy integratsiyasini osonlashtiradi.

Demak, individual ta'limning pedagogik ahamiyati talabalarning shaxsiy o'sishini, o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish, ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash, inklyuziv ta'lim imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilganligida namoyon bo'ladi.

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СИСТЕМА РАБОТЫ ПО ОБУЧЕНИЮ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ ПО РЕЧЕВОМУ ЭТИКЕТУ НА УРОКАХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА И ВНЕУРОЧНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается система работы по формированию и развитию навыков речевого этикета у школьников на уроках русского языка и во внеурочной деятельности. Подчеркивается значимость речевого этикета как важного элемента общей культуры личности и коммуникативной компетенции учащихся. Особое внимание уделяется комплексному подходу к обучению, включающему использование разнообразных методов и приёмов: игровые технологии, моделирование речевых ситуаций, ролевые игры, диалоги, инсценировки. Представлены формы организации внеурочной работы – кружки, конкурсы, театрализованные постановки, внеклассные мероприятия. Описанная система способствует формированию у школьников устойчивых норм речевого поведения и развитию культуры общения.

Ключевые слова: речевой этикет, русский язык, школьники, урок, внеурочная деятельность, коммуникативная компетенция.

Актуальность данной темы определяется необходимостью повышения уровня речевой культуры учащихся, формирования у них устойчивых навыков этичного речевого поведения и развития коммуникативной компетенции как важнейшей составляющей успешной социализации в обществе.

Современное образование ориентировано не только на передачу знаний, но и на развитие у учащихся коммуникативных умений, культуры речи и навыков эффективного взаимодействия в обществе. Одним из важнейших компонентов коммуникативной компетенции является речевой этикет – совокупность языковых средств и правил речевого поведения, отражающих нормы вежливости и культурного общения. В условиях многонациональной и поликультурной среды владение речевым этикетом становится особенно актуальным. Школа играет ключевую роль в формировании речевой культуры личности, так как именно в школьные годы закладываются основы правильного и этичного речевого поведения. Уроки русского языка обладают большими возможностями для системной работы в данном направлении: через изучение языковых единиц, диалогов, текстов и практических заданий формируются устойчивые навыки речевого общения.

Не менее важное место занимает внеурочная деятельность, которая дополняет и расширяет учебный процесс. Кружки, конкурсы чтецов, театральные постановки, лингвистические игры и творческие проекты позволяют закреплять и развивать умения использовать нормы речевого этикета в реальных и игровых ситуациях. Разработка и внедрение целостной системы обучения школьников речевому этикету как на уроках русского языка, так и во внеурочной работе является одной из актуальных задач современной методики преподавания.

Методология исследования. В данной статье исследования составляют современные достижения педагогической науки, лингвистики и методики преподавания русского языка, а также принципы личностно-ориентированного, коммуникативного и деятельностного подходов к обучению.

Речевой этикет – это установленная система норм и формул вежливого общения, принятых в обществе. Он охватывает обращения, приветствия, прощания, выражения благодарности, извинения, просьбы, согласия, отказа и другие речевые действия.

Изучение речевого этикета способствует формированию у школьников коммуникативной гибкости, способности учитывать адресата и ситуацию общения, развивает чувство языка и уважение к культурным традициям.

Уроки русского языка являются основной площадкой для обучения речевому этикету. В рамках программы целесообразно включать:

- анализ речевых ситуаций – разбор диалогов с точки зрения уместности и вежливости;
- ролевые игры – моделирование общения (в магазине, в школе, в транспорте и т.д.);
- упражнения и инсценировки – закрепление формул речевого этикета в устной и письменной речи;
- интеграцию с темами уроков – использование речевых формул в заданиях по орфографии, синтаксису, чтению и письму.

Такая работа формирует у учащихся практические умения культурного речевого поведения [1, с 89].

Внеурочные формы работы дают возможность закрепить знания и умения в неформальной обстановке. Наиболее эффективными являются:

- кружки и клубы общения, где школьники обсуждают разные темы, тренируются использовать речевые формулы в свободной речи.
- конкурсы, викторины и театрализованные мероприятия, которые развивают творческие способности и умение применять речевой этике различных ситуациях.
- проекты и праздники вежливости, способствующие активному вовлечению учащихся и повышению интереса к культуре общения.

Эти формы создают условия для естественного и осознанного использования речевого этикета [4, с 103].

Наблюдение за речевым поведением учащихся в различных ситуациях общения. Текущие и итоговые диагностики уровня владения речевым этикетом (опросники, тесты, практические задания). Ведение «речевого портфолио» ученика с фиксацией достижений. Анализ результатов и внесение изменений в систему работы при необходимости.

Методы и приёмы обучения речевому этикету школьников:

- ✓ **объяснительно-иллюстративный метод** – знакомство с речевыми формулами через примеры из художественной литературы, диалоги, пословицы;
- ✓ **практические методы** – устные упражнения, ролевые игры, разыгрывание речевых ситуаций (в магазине, в школе, на улице, в гостях и т.д.);
- ✓ **игровые методы** – использование сюжетно-ролевых игр, конкурсов вежливости, викторин, квестов;
- ✓ **метод проектов** – создание мини-проектов (например, «этикет в нашей школе»), разработка памяток по вежливому общению;
- ✓ **информационно-коммуникационные технологии (икт)** – использование презентаций, видеороликов, интерактивных заданий.

Таким образом, формирование речевого этикета у школьников – важная и актуальная задача современного образования. Системный подход, объединяющий урочную и внеурочную деятельность, позволяет не только познакомить учащихся с нормами речевого поведения, но и закрепить их на практике. Результатом такой работы становится развитие коммуникативной компетенции, повышение культуры речи,

формирование уважительного отношения к собеседнику и языку. Это, в свою очередь, способствует успешной социализации и гармоничному развитию личности.

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ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ЛАБИРИНТЕ ТЕКСТА: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИИ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

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Аннотация. В настоящей статье рассматривается двойственная роль технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в современной дидактике литературы. Анализируются ключевые преимущества внедрения ИИ, включая персонализацию учебного процесса, повышение эффективности рутинных задач (оценка, подбор материала) и возможности для глубокого, стилометрического анализа текста. Одновременно с этим исследуются и критические недостатки, в частности, угроза академической недобросовестности, риск снижения когнитивных и эмпатических навыков чтения, а также проблема "черного ящика" в интерпретации текста. Делается вывод о необходимости переосмысления педагогической парадигмы в сторону развития ИИ-грамотности и критического мышления как основной задачи литературоведения в цифровую эпоху.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, преподавание литературы, цифровая педагогика, анализ текста, критическое мышление, академическая этика, гуманитарные науки.

Образование в области литературы всегда находилось на пересечении традиции и инноваций, между рукописью и печатным словом, между тишиной библиотеки и шумом публичных чтений. Основная цель нашего предмета – развитие глубинного понимания человеческого опыта, критического анализа и словесной выразительности. В последние годы перед нами встал вызов, сравнимый по своей тектонической силе лишь с изобретением Гутенберга: повсеместное внедрение генеративного искусственного интеллекта (ИИ).

Искусственный интеллект, в лице больших языковых моделей (LLM), уже способен не просто писать, но и имитировать глубокие эссе, анализировать стилистику и даже генерировать поэтические тексты с пугающей убедительностью. Этот прорыв неизбежно меняет не только способы, которыми студенты пишут о литературе, но и то, как они ее читают. Он ставит нас перед зеркалом, в котором отражается вопрос: что остается от искусства интерпретации, когда машина может сгенерировать интерпретацию в тысячу раз быстрее человека? Целью данной статьи является прагматический анализ ИИ с точки зрения преподавателя-практика, сфокусированный на определении реальных преимуществ и стратегических недостатков, чтобы мы могли не плыть по течению, но прокладывать курс в этом новом, алгоритмическом океане.

Мы должны видеть в ИИ не врага, а мощнейший инструмент, способный снять с плеч педагога бремя рутины и открыть новые горизонты анализа. Традиционный класс неизбежно ограничен унифицированными заданиями, словно предлагая один и тот же наряд для всех. ИИ позволяет создать по-настоящему адаптивный учебный маршрут, который учитывает уникальные лакуны в знаниях каждого студента.

Пример: Студент отлично справляется с фабулой романа Л.Н. Толстого «Война и мир», но демонстрирует непонимание концепции «народной мысли» и функций несобственно-прямой речи. ИИ, проанализировав предыдущие работы, может сгенерировать не стандартный вопрос по сюжету, а серию узконаправленных сократических диалогов, требующих объяснить, как внутренняя речь князя Андрея отражает этическую позицию автора, тем самым фокусируясь на навыке филологической тонкости, а не на пересказе. Это позволяет преподавателю освободить время для менторства, а не для механической проверки.

Искусственный интеллект открывает двери в область Цифровых Гуманитарных Наук (Digital Humanities), предлагая инструменты для углубленного текстового анализа, выходящего за пределы возможностей человеческого глаза. ИИ способен за считанные секунды проводить стилометрический анализ огромных корпусов текстов, выявляя скрытые лингвистические паттерны, которые сознанию недоступны. Например, используя ИИ, можно провести количественный анализ частотности использования метафор, связанных с морем и светом, в ранних и поздних произведениях В. Набокова. Это позволяет эмпирически подтвердить или опровергнуть интуитивные догадки исследователя о динамике его стиля. Подобный анализ становится ценным дополнением к герменевтике, обогащая субъективную интерпретацию объективными, статистически подтвержденными данными.

Снижение рутинной нагрузки: автоматизация рутинных задач – это не просто экономия времени, это возвращение преподавателю его творческого начала. ИИ может взять на себя черновую работу: первичное рецензирование студенческих эссе на предмет грамматики и логической структуры, подбор цитат для иллюстрирования тезисов или создание разнообразных контрольных материалов. Сокращение времени, потраченного на механику языка, позволяет педагогу сосредоточиться на алхимии смысла – разработке креативных, провокационных заданий и фасилитации сложных, многослойных дискуссий в аудитории.

Наряду с блестящими перспективами, ИИ несет в себе глубокие, экзистенциальные угрозы для самой природы нашего предмета. Самый острый вызов – это использование генеративного ИИ для создания письменных работ. Мы столкнулись с кризисом интеллектуальной аутентичности. Если ИИ способен создать убедительное, логически безупречное эссе по «Гамлету» за минуту, теряется весь образовательный смысл. Это ведет к эрозии фундаментальных когнитивных навыков:

умения искать, сомневаться, структурировать собственный, выстраданный аргумент. Мы получаем работы, обладающие синтетической компетентностью, но лишённые подлинной любознательности и индивидуального голоса.

Преподаватель теперь вынужден разрабатывать «Сократические задания», которые ИИ не может решить: задания, требующие моментальной реакции, защиты тезиса в реальном времени, обращения к личному опыту или неожиданного сопоставления контекстов. Например, сравните мотив мести в трагедии Шекспира и в вашем любимом современном сериале и объясните этическую разницу, защитив свое мнение устно.

Искусственный интеллект интерпретирует текст не на основе понимания, а на основе статистических вероятностей и языковых паттернов. Он не переживает, не испытывает страха или радости, и не способен постичь человеческий субъективизм и эмоциональный подтекст, который является квинтэссенцией литературы. Полагаясь на ИИ, мы рискуем навязать студентам обезличенную, алгоритмически усредненную интерпретацию, основанную на данных, а не на критическом суждении. Проблема: ИИ может проанализировать, сколько раз в романе Ф.М. Достоевского «Преступление и наказание» упоминается желтый цвет Петербурга (как цвет болезни и безумия). Но он не может взвесить моральную тяжесть преступления Родиона Раскольникова, не может почувствовать его метафизическое одиночество. Использование ИИ без критической оценки превращает литературу в «алгоритмический мираж» – иллюзию понимания, за которой скрывается пустота. Кроме того, обученный на англосаксонских корпусах, ИИ часто проявляет алгоритмическую предвзятость, неточно интерпретируя тексты из других культурных ареалов, искажая, например, тон японской поэзии или африканского эпоса.

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RUS TILINI O'RGANISHDAGI PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada rus tilini o'rganish jarayonida o'quvchilarning psixologik xususiyatlari, ularning individual qobiliyatlari, motivatsiya, xotira, tafakkur, diqqat kabi psixik jarayonlarning roli, shuningdek, o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati va psixologik yondashuvining ahamiyati yoritiladi. Til o'rganishda kommunikativ yondashuv, motivatsiyani shakllantirish, ijobiy o'quv muhitini yaratish va psixologik to'siqlarni bartaraf etish yo'llari haqida ilmiy asoslangan fikrlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: rus tili, psixologik xususiyat, motivatsiya, diqqat, xotira, tafakkur, kommunikativ yondashuv, psixologik muhit, ta'lim samaradorligi.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida xorijiy tillarni, jumladan rus tilini bilish har bir mutaxassis uchun zaruriy ehtiyojga aylanmoqda. Rus tili xalqaro ilmiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy muloqotda muhim o'rin tutadi. Shu bois uni o'rganish jarayonida nafaqat metodik, balki psixologik omillar ham katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Rus tili - boy tarixga, chuqur madaniyatga ega til. Uni o'rganish faqat grammatikani bilish emas, balki rus xalqi madaniyati, adabiyoti va tafakkur tarzini tushunishni ham anglatadi. Rus tili o'zining talaffuzi, so'z boyligi va ifoda imkoniyatlari bilan boshqa tillardan farq qiladi. Uni o'rganish menda sabr, e'tibor va tahliliy fikrlashni shakllantiradi. Har bir yangi so'z yoki ibora men uchun yangi dunyoga eshik ochadi.

Rus tili o'rganish o'quvchilarda ijodiy fikrlashni, tahliliy yondashuvni va madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Shu bois, bu tilni o'rganish nafaqat lingvistik, balki ijtimoiy va shaxsiy rivojlanish uchun ham zarur hisoblanadi.

Til o'rganish - bu murakkab psixik faoliyat bo'lib, unda diqqat, xotira, tafakkur, idrok va nutq jarayonlari faol ishtirok etadi. O'quvchi yangi tilni o'zlashtirishda sezgi organlari orqali ma'lumotni qabul qiladi, so'ngra u ongda qayta ishlanadi va nutq shakliga aylanadi. Shu bois o'qituvchi vizual, audial va kinestetik usullarni uyg'unlashtirgan holda foydalanishi zarur, lozim[1]. Bugungi kunda o'quvchi chet tili darslarini o'zlashtira olmayotgan holatlarni ushbu masala bilan bog'liq bir qator muammolar keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Til o'rganishning va uni o'rgatishning psixologik o'ziga xosligi chet tilidagi matnni idrok etish, chet tilidagi so'zlarni xotirada saqlash bilan xorijiy til o'quvchilari chet tilini o'zlashtirishi jarayonida ularning o'ziga tildagi tafakkuri kengayib borishini ta'minlashning psixologik jihatlarini bilishni talab qiladi. O'qituvchi xorijiy tilda talabalarning rivojlanishiga xos bo'lgan psixologik xususiyatlarni o'rganishi, o'quvchilar aqliy taraqqiyotining psixologik qonuniyatlaridan xabardor bo'lishi, talabalarning psixologik taraqqiyotiga faol ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganishi ular bilan bo'ladigan munosabatlar uchun zarur psixologik ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga oladi[2].

Xorijiy tilda talabalarning chet tilida mustaqil, erkin fikrlash doirasini kengaytirish, ular bilan suhbatlarni to'g'ri tashkil eta olishga ham bog'liq. O'quv jarayonini tashkil etish. O'qitish jarayonini tashkil etar ekan, o'qituvchi ta'lim tamoyilini qo'llashi, o'qitishning psixologik jihatlariga e'tibor berishi va o'qitish materiali va uslubini o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishiga moslashtirishi kerak. Tilni muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirish jarayonining navbatdagi bosqichi o'quvchilarning diqqatini jalb qiladi. Materialni yaxshiroq taqdim etish va uni o'quvchilar tomonidan o'zlashtirishi uchun o'qituvchi ham diqqatni yo'naltirish jarayoni va berilgan dars materialini o'zlashtirish jarayoni bilan bog'liq bo'lgan psixologik nazariya bilan tanishishi kerak. Bundan tashqari, har bir o'qituvchi uchun o'quvchilarning diqqatini jamlash juda muhimdir. Buning uchun o'qituvchi turli xil o'qitish usullaridan foydalanadi. Shunday qilib, ko'rgazmali yordamni aniq vaqtda qo'llash bu holatda katta yordam beradi. O'qituvchi bir necha daqiqadan so'ng o'quvchilarning e'tiborini yo'qotmaslik uchun g'amxo'rlik qilishi kerak. Vizual yordamni o'z vaqtida ishlatish juda muhim, aks holda ta'sir butunlay teskari bo'ladi. Masalan, dars boshida sinf oldiga osilgan rasm yoki biron bir

stol ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatmaydi, chunki o'quvchilar buni allaqachon ko'rgan va ularning diqqati bir vaqtning o'zida to'planmaydi. Bunday holda, ko'rgazmali yordamni o'z vaqtida ishlatmaslik salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Motivatsiya - til o'rganishning yuragi hisoblanadi. O'quvchi nimaga bu tilni o'rganayotganini anglasa, o'qishga bo'lgan ishtiyoq kuchayadi. Ichki motivatsiya shaxsiy qiziqish bilan, tashqi motivatsiya esa baho yoki rag'bat bilan bog'liq. O'qituvchi ichki motivatsiyani rag'batlantirishi zarur[3]. Motivatsiyani shakllantirishda o'qituvchining roli beqiyosdir. Yaxshi o'qituvchi darsni faqat bilim berish emas, balki ilhomlantirish jarayoni sifatida olib boradi. Interfaol metodlar, o'yinlar, ijodiy topshiriqlar, muloqot mashqlari talabalarda tilga bo'lgan ishtiyoqni kuchaytiradi[4]. Umuman olganda til o'rganishda motivatsiya - bu muvaffaqiyat kalitidir. O'quvchi o'zida qiziqish, maqsad va ishonchni shakllantira olsa, u har qanday tilni oson o'zlashtira oladi. O'qituvchi esa bu jarayonni to'g'ri yo'naltirishi, rag'batlantirishi va ijobiy psixologik muhit yaratishi zarur. Shunday sharoitda til o'rganish nafaqat bilim olish, balki o'zini rivojlantirish yo'lida katta qadam bo'ladi

Til o'rganishda diqqatning barqarorligi muhim. Interaktiv mashg'ulotlar, o'yin usullari diqqatni kuchaytiradi. Xotira esa yangi so'z va grammatikani eslab qolishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Darslarda faol ishtirok eslab qolishni yaxshilaydi.

Til inson tafakkurining eng muhim vositasidir. Tafakkur - bu insonning atrof-muhitdagi hodisalarni anglash, tahlil qilish va xulosa chiqarish jarayonidir. Til esa bu tafakkurning ifoda shakli, ya'ni inson o'z fikrini tilda ifoda etish orqali uni boshqalar bilan bo'lishadi. Shu sababdan, tafakkur va til bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'langan hodisalar bo'lib, ularning uyg'unligi til o'rganish jarayonida hal qiluvchi o'rin tutadi.

Rus tilini o'rganish jarayonida mantiqiy tafakkur rivojlanadi. Gap tuzish, matn tahlili tafakkurni o'stiradi. Til va tafakkur o'zaro chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, til tafakkurni shakllantiradi. Tafakkur va til o'rganish uyg'unligi psixologik tayyorgarlikni ham talab etadi. O'quvchi o'z tafakkurini yangi tildagi fikr tuzilmasiga moslashtirishi uchun motivatsiya, xotira va diqqat kabi psixik jarayonlar muhim o'rin tutadi.

Psixologik to'siqlar va ularni bartaraf etish

O'quvchilar ko'pincha xatodan qo'rqish yoki uyalish kabi to'siqlarga duch keladi. O'qituvchi do'stona muhit yaratib, xatolarni muloyimlik bilan tuzatishi kerak. Rolli o'yinlar, guruh mashg'ulotlari ishonchni oshiradi. Agarda bola tilni o'rganishda qanaqadir noqulaylikni his etsa bu ko'nikmalarni o'zlashtirishda juda katta to'siqlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bu to'siqlarni bartaraf etishda umuman mavjud bo'lishligiga yo'l qo'ymaslik albatta o'qituvchidan yaxshi bilim va ko'nikma yetarli darajada bo'lishi ayni kun haqiqati o'raloq qabul qilinadi. ana endi mavjud to'siqlar va ularga bo'ladigan yechimlar haqida bir necha misollar:

Xatodan qo'rqish: Ko'pchilik o'quvchilar rus tilida gapirishdan uyalishadi yoki xato qilishdan qo'rqishadi. Ular "agar men noto'g'ri gapirsam, boshqalar kuladi" degan o'y bilan o'z fikrini bildirishdan tiyilishadi. Yechim: Xatolarni o'rganish jarayonining tabiiy qismi sifatida qabul qilish kerak. Har bir xato - bu o'sish va to'g'ri variantni o'rganish imkoniyati. O'ziga ishonchsizlik: O'quvchi "men hech qachon rus tilini o'rganolmayman" degan salbiy fikrni shakllantirsa, bu tilni egallashga katta to'siqlik qiladi. Yechim: Har bir kichik yutuqni qadrlash, o'zini rag'batlantirish muhim. Kichik gaplar tuzish, oson matnlarni o'qish orqali o'ziga ishonchni mustahkamlash kerak. Motivatsiyaning pastligi: Til o'rganishdagi psixologik to'siqlarning eng asosiylaridan biri - motivatsiyaning yo'qligi yoki pasayishi. Yechim: Tilni o'rganishdan maqsadni aniq belgilash zarur. Masalan, "rus tilini bilsam, kelajakda yaxshi ish topaman" yoki "rus tilida film tomosha qilmoqchiman" kabi maqsadlar motivatsiyani kuchaytiradi. Stress va bosim: Ba'zi hollarda o'qituvchi yoki sinfdoshlarning bosimi tufayli

o'quvchi o'zini noqulay his qiladi. Bu esa fikrni erkin ifoda etish imkonini cheklaydi. Yechim: O'quv muhitida do'stona atmosfera yaratish, qo'llab-quvvatlash muhim. O'quvchini tanqid qilish o'rniga, rag'batlantirish kerak. Til muhitining yo'qligi: Agar o'quvchi rus tilida muloqot qilmasa, u o'z bilimini amalda qo'llay olmaydi, bu esa o'zini "bilmayman" degan hisga olib keladi. Yechim: Rus tilidagi filmlar, musiqalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali o'rganish jarayonini jonlantirish mumkin.

O'qituvchining psixologik yondashuvi

O'qituvchining shaxsiyati til o'rgatishda hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. U rag'batlantiruvchi muhit yaratishi, o'quvchilarning holatini tushunishi va emotsional muvozanatni saqlashi zarur. O'qituvchi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki o'quvchi ruhiyatini tushunuvchi, uni rag'batlantiruvchi shaxsdir. Rus tili o'rganishda ko'pchilik o'quvchilar nutqiy xatolardan qo'rqish, o'z fikrini erkin aytolmaslik, tilda xatoga yo'l qo'yishdan uyalish kabi psixologik to'siqlarga duch keladi. Shu bois o'qituvchi o'quvchining ichki holatini sezib, unga individual yondashishi lozim. O'qituvchi darsda doim ij

O'qituvchi darsda doim ijobiy, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhitni shakllantirishi kerak. O'quvchilarni tanqid qilish o'rniga, ularning harakatini qadrlash, kichik yutuqlarini ham e'tirof etish muhimdir. Ijobiy emotsional muhit o'quvchilarda o'zini erkin tutish va tilda faol muloqotga kirishishga yordam beradi. Har bir o'quvchining o'rganish tezligi, psixologik xususiyatlari, tilda fikrlash qobiliyati turlicha. O'qituvchi buni inobatga olib, kimlargadir ko'proq og'zaki mashqlar, kimlargadir esa yozma topshiriqlar berishi mumkin. Bu yondashuv o'quvchilarning ichki ishonchini oshiradi va shu yo'l bilan natijani samadorligini oshirishi mumkin[7].

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РАЗВИТИЕ РЕЧЕВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ КАК СРЕДСТВО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается актуальная проблема развития речевой культуры школьников как ключевого условия и средства обеспечения их коммуникативной активности. Подчеркивается, что в условиях модернизации образования и социального запроса на формирование компетентной и социально активной личности владения высокой культурой речи становится важнейшей составляющей коммуникативной компетентности. Анализируются теоретические аспекты взаимосвязи понятий культура речи и коммуникативная активность. Автор раскрывает структуру и основные качества культуры речи (нормативность и уместность, логичность, богатство), прямо влияющие на способность учащегося вступать в продуктивный диалог, выражать свои мысли четко и убедительно, и, как следствие, на его готовность к активной коммуникативной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: речевая культура, коммуникативная активность. Коммуникативная компетентность, школьники, развитие речи, устная речь, педагогические условия.

Современное общество, характеризующееся высокой динамичностью социальных процессов, глобализацией и интенсивным развитием информационных технологий, предъявляет новые требования к личности, вступающей в жизнь. Одним из ключевых условий успешной самореализации, социального взаимодействия и профессиональной деятельности является сформированная коммуникативная компетентность. Она, в свою очередь, неразрывно связана с уровнем речевой культуры личности.

Система общего образования призвана подготовить выпускника, способного к активному, осознанному и продуктивному общению. Однако анализ педагогической практики и исследований показывает наличие противоречия: с одной стороны, существует социальный запрос на активную, свободно владеющую словом личность, с другой – отмечается недостаточный уровень речевой культуры и, как следствие, низкая коммуникативная активность значительной части школьников. Многие учащиеся испытывают трудности в построении связного монологического и диалогического высказывания, в соблюдении норм литературного языка и в выборе уместных языковых средств в различных ситуациях общения. Таким образом, проблема развития речевой культуры школьников как средства обеспечения их коммуникативной активности приобретает особую актуальность в контексте реализации федеральных государственных образовательных стандартов, ориентированных на формирование личностных, метапредметных и предметных результатов.

Проблема развития речи традиционно находится в центре внимания отечественной педагогики, лингвистики и психологии. Теоретические основы речевой культуры заложены в трудах таких ученых, как В. В. Виноградов, Л. И. Скворцов, О. Б. Сиротинина. Вопросы коммуникативной активности и компетентности разрабатывались в работах А. А. Леонтьева, и. А. Зимней, Ю. М. Жукова и других. Методические аспекты развития речи школьников освещены в исследованиях М. Р. Львова, Т. А. Ладыженской, И. А. Ипполитовой. Тем не менее, комплексное исследование механизмов, посредством которых повышение речевой культуры напрямую стимулирует и обеспечивает коммуникативную активность учащихся в условиях современной образовательной среды, остается недостаточно разработанным.

Теоретически обосновано, что речевая культура, понимаемая как единство нормативного, коммуникативного и этического аспектов, является ключевым механизмом и средством обеспечения коммуникативной активности школьников. Установлено, что высокий уровень владения культурой речи снижает психологический барьер и повышает мотивацию к активному речевому взаимодействию.

Разработаны практические методические рекомендации для учителей по внедрению в образовательный процесс коммуникативно-деятельностного подхода, направленного на интегративное развитие речевой культуры и коммуникативной активности школьников.

Проведенный анализ подтвердил теоретическую гипотезу о том, что речевая культура не является лишь набором лингвистических норм, но представляет собой интегративное личностное качество, напрямую влияющее на мотивационно-поведенческий компонент коммуникативной активности.

Культура речи как устранение барьеров: обсуждается, что владение нормативным и этическим аспектами речи (точность, уместность, вежливость) снижает уровень тревожности и страха публичных выступлений у школьников. Уверенность в правильности и корректности своей речи является мощным стимулом для добровольного вступления в коммуникацию. Неумение же правильно выражать мысль часто приводит к коммуникативному ступору и избегания общения.

Подчеркивается, что логический аспект речевой культуры (умение строить аргументацию, выстраивать связный текст) напрямую обеспечивает продуктивность коммуникативной активности. Школьник умеющий логично излагать свои мысли, будет более активен в дискуссиях в дебатах, поскольку видит реальный результат своего усилия. Полученные положительные статистические результаты в экспериментальных группах убедительно доказывает эффективность предложенного комплекса педагогических условий.

Речевая культура является эффективным и необходимым средством для обеспечения и повышения коммуникативной активности школьников. Экспериментально доказана эффективность разработанных педагогических условий. Достижение высокого уровня культуры речи устраняет психологические барьеры и стимулирует учащихся к активному, осознанному и продуктивному общению. Развитие речевой культуры следует рассматривать как ключевой приоритет для подготовки компетентной и социально активной личности.

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AMALIY KO'NIKMALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI VOSITALARNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) jadal rivojlanib borayotgan bir davrda ta'lim tizimida ham yangi yondashuvlar va metodikalar joriy etilmoqda. Ayniqsa, oliy ta'lim muassasalarida **Davlat tilida ish yuritish** kabi amaliy fanlarni o'qitishda raqamli vositalardan foydalanish zarurati ortib bormoqda. Ushbu maqolada raqamli texnologiyalar muhitida Davlat tilida ish yuritish kursini o'qitishning dolzarbligi, metodik yondashuvlari va pedagogik afzalliklari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat tili, ish yuritish, raqamli texnologiya, zamonaviy texnologiya.

Davlat tilida ish yuritish - bu hujjatlarni rasmiy tilda, ya'ni o'zbek tilida yuritish bo'yicha nazariy va amaliy bilimlarni o'z ichiga oluvchi kurs bo'lib, talabalarni professional muhitda rasmiy hujjatlar bilan ishlash ko'nikmalariga o'rgatadi. Bu kurs orqali talabalar:

- ish yuritish normalari va standartlarini o'zlashtiradilar;
- rasmiy-stilistik me'yorlarga rioya qilishni o'rganadilar;
- elektron hujjat aylanishi va axborot tizimlarida ishlash ko'nikmalarini egallaydilar[1].

Raqamli texnologiyalar o'quv jarayonini soddalashtirish, optimallashtirish va individuallashtirishda keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Ayniqsa, Davlat tilida ish yuritish fanida bu texnologiyalar orqali amaliy va didaktik afzalliklar ta'minlanadi. Bugungi kunda o'quv jarayonini masofadan tashkil qilish uchun bir qator raqamli platformalar joriy etilgan:

- Google Classroom, Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Ziyonet LMS kabi platformalar orqali o'quv materiallarini joylashtirish, uy vazifalarini topshirish va teskari aloqani tashkil etish mumkin.
- Dars jarayonlari videodarslar, vebinarlar shaklida o'tkazilib, talabalar istalgan vaqtda ularga qaytib murojaat qilish imkoniga ega bo'ladi.

Bu imkoniyatlar talabaning o'quv jarayonida mustaqilligini kuchaytiradi, moslashuvchan ta'lim muhitini yaratadi[4].

Raqamli ta'limda matnli ma'lumotlardan tashqari, quyidagi vositalar katta ahamiyatga ega:

- Slayd-prezentatsiyalar: hujjatlar tuzilmasi, ularning rasmiy-stilistik xususiyatlarini vizual ko'rsatishda qulay.
- Interaktiv testlar va viktorinalar: masalan, Google Forms, Kahoot, Quizizz kabi platformalar orqali talabalar bilimni real vaqt rejimida baholash mumkin.
- Video darslar: til me'yorlarini tushuntiruvchi videolar orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish.

Talaba matnni nafaqat o'qiydi, balki eshitadi, ko'radi va interaktiv muloqotga kirishadi. Bu esa bilimning mustahkam o'zlashtirilishini ta'minlaydi. Davlat tilida ish yuritish kursining asosiy maqsadlaridan biri - talabani elektron hujjatlar aylanishiga tayyorlashdir. Bu borada raqamli texnologiyalar quyidagi imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi:

- Microsoft Word, Excel, Google Docs kabi dasturlar yordamida amaliy topshiriqlarni bajarish (buyruqlar, farmoyishlar, bayonnomalar tuzish).

- Raqamli imzo, QR-kod va skanerlash vositalari bilan ishlash bo'yicha ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish.
- My.gov.uz, e-ijro.gov.uz, hisobot.uz kabi portallar orqali hujjat topshirish, ariza yozish, murojaat qilish bo'yicha mashqlar bajarish.

Bu orqali talaba nafaqat til me'yorlarini, balki real ish muhiti uchun zarur bo'lgan ijtimoiy-axboriy savodxonlikni ham egallaydi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida o'quvchilar quyidagi interaktiv imkoniyatlardan foydalanishlari mumkin:

- Imlo va grammatik xatoliklarni aniqlovchi tizimlar (Grammarly, LanguageTool, imlo.uz);
- Til korpuslari orqali so'z birikmalari, atamalarni o'rganish;
- AI asosidagi matn tuzish vositalari yordamida hujjatlar andozalarini avtomatik shakllantirish;
- Tovushli buyruq tizimlari orqali matnni tinglash, eslatmalarni qayd qilish[4].

Bularning barchasi davlat tilida ish yuritishni nafaqat o'rganish, balki undan innovatsion tarzda foydalanishni ham rag'batlantiradi. Raqamli muhitda Davlat tilida ish yuritish fanini samarali o'qitish uchun zamonaviy metodik yondashuvlar qo'llanilishi lozim. An'anaviy va innovatsion metodlarning uyg'unligi o'quv jarayonini qiziqarli va samarali qiladi:

- **Konstruktiv yondashuv**- talabani dars jarayonining faol ishtirokchisiga aylantirish:
 - Hujjatlarni o'zi mustaqil tuzadi;
 - O'rganilgan me'yorlar asosida o'z bahosini beradi;
 - Matnlar ustida tahliliy fikrlaydi.

Bu metod orqali talabada muammoli vaziyatlarda yechim topish, ijodiy fikrlash ko'nikmalari shakllanadi.

- **Gibrid (blended) ta'lim modeli**- ushbu yondashuvda an'anaviy auditoriya darslari bilan onlayn ta'lim shakllari uyg'unlashtiriladi. Masalan:

- Nazariy ma'lumotlar - videodarslar orqali beriladi;
- Amaliy topshiriqlar - auditoriyada bajariladi;
- Mustaqil ishlar - onlayn platformalarda taqdim etiladi.

Bu model ta'lim jarayonini moslashuvchan, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan qiladi.

- **Case-study yondashuvi**- real hayotdan olingan misollar asosida hujjat tahlili:

- Talabalar sud hujjatlari, qarorlar, buyruqlar matni bilan ishlaydi;
- Hujjatlarda yo'l qo'yilgan xatolarni aniqlaydi;
- O'z yechimlarini taklif qiladi.

Bu usul talabani professional kontekstga tayyorlaydi va mehnat muhitida duch keladigan vaziyatlarga moslashtiradi.

- **Gamifikatsiya (ta'limiy o'yinlar elementlari)**- ta'limda o'yin elementlarini qo'llash orqali:

- Rag'bat tizimi (ball, reyting, sertifikatlar);
- Topsiriqlarni bajarishda musobaqaviylik;
- Rol o'yinlari: "muassasa kotibi", "kadrlar bo'limi xodimi", "boshqarma rahbari" rollarida hujjat tayyorlash.

Bu orqali talabalar mavzuni qiziqish bilan o'zlashtiradi va motivatsiyasi ortadi.

- **Peer-review va kollaborativ o'qitish**-talabalar o'zaro guruhlarda ishlaydi:

- Bir-birining ishini tekshiradi, taklif beradi;
- Hujjat tahlili va tahririni jamoaviy muhokama qiladi;
- Elektron hujjat aylanishini simulyatsiya qiladi.

Bu esa ko'p fikrlilik, tahlil qilish, baholash va samarali muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi.

Raqamli muhitda o'qitishda quyidagi muammolar uchrashi mumkin:

- AKT vositalarini yetarli darajada bilmaslik;
- Texnik infratuzilmaning sust rivojlanganligi;
- O'quv materiallarining elektron shaklda yetarli emasligi.

Bu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun quyidagilarni taklif etishni maqsadga muvofiq:

- O'qituvchilar uchun AKT bo'yicha malaka oshirish kurslarini joriy etish;
- Davlat tilida ish yuritish bo'yicha interaktiv, multimediya vositalarini ishlab chiqish;
- Onlayn hujjatlar bazasini yaratish va unga ochiq kirishni ta'minlash.

Raqamli texnologiyalar muhitida Davlat tilida ish yuritish kursini o'qitish - zamonaviy ta'limning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, talabalar bilimini oshirish, amaliy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish va ularni mehnat bozorida raqobatbardosh qilishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Raqamli vositalarni to'g'ri va samarali qo'llash orqali ushbu kursni yangi bosqichga olib chiqish, uni innovatsion ta'limga moslashtirish mumkin. Bu esa nafaqat ta'lim sifatini oshiradi, balki davlat tilining amaliyotdagi mavqeini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

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РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ И САМООБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается необходимость применения информационных технологий на занятиях по русскому языку и литературе. Подчеркивается, что использование информационных технологий способствует совершенствованию практических навыков, эффективной организации самостоятельной работы учащихся, индивидуализация учебного процесса, а также повышает интерес к предмету, активизирует познавательную деятельность и делает учебные занятия более современными.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, актуальные проблемы, компьютерная технология, внедрение, формирование, навыки, цифровизация, самообразование.

Современное общество, находясь в фазе интенсивной цифровой трансформации, ставит перед системой образования новые задачи. Одной из ключевых характеристик современного образовательного пространства становится активное внедрение ИТ (информационных технологий), кардинально меняющих как содержание обучения, так и формы его организации. Информатизация образования является одним из важнейших условий успешного развития процессов информатизации общества, поскольку именно в образовательной среде формируются специалисты, призванные не только создавать

и развивать информационную инфраструктуру, но и полноценно функционировать в условиях цифровой реальности [1, с. 24].

Под информационными технологиями понимают комплекс научных и прикладных дисциплин, ориентированных на создание и применение эффективных решений для обработки, хранения и передачи данных посредством компьютерных средств. Они охватывают не только технические аспекты взаимодействия человека с вычислительной техникой, но и затрагивают социальные, экономические и культурные аспекты цифровизации труда и производства.

Ключевыми характеристиками современных информационных технологий выступают возможность автоматизированной обработки данных, сохранение значительных объёмов информации на цифровых носителях, а также мгновенная передача этих данных на любые расстояния. Эти особенности обеспечивают принципиально новые условия для организации образовательного процесса.

Достижение высоких результатов в изучении русского языка возможно лишь при условии его глубокого включения в образовательную среду. Это означает, что преподавание языка должно быть неотъемлемой частью общего воспитательного процесса. Особую роль в этом играет согласованная работа педагогического коллектива, нацеленная на формирование у обучающихся устойчивых навыков грамотной устной и письменной речи, а также создание благоприятной речевой атмосферы, стимулирующей постоянную практику общения на русском языке.

Эффективное средство активизации познавательной, рефлексивной деятельности обучающихся – это использование ИТ в образовательном и самообразовательном процессе. Основные преимущества инновационных технологий позволяют разнообразить формы работы, деятельность обучающихся, активизировать внимание, повышает творческий потенциал личности. ИКТ(информационно-коммуникационные технологии) активизирует процесс обучения: повышает темп занятия, позволяет проверить усвоение теории, углубить степень отработки практических умений и навыков, вести дифференцированную работу с каждым студентом. Использование ИКТ в образовательном процессе оправдано на разных этапах обучения и способствует его качественному улучшению. На этапе объяснения нового материала особенно эффективны визуальные и справочные цифровые ресурсы, которые позволяют подать информацию более наглядно и доступно. В процессе закрепления изученного целесообразно применять интерактивные обучающие программы и тренажёры, направленные на повторение и практическое применение знаний. Для контроля усвоения материала ИКТ могут быть представлены в виде тестирующих систем, автоматически оценивающих ответы и позволяющих оперативно выявить пробелы в знаниях. Важно и то, что с их помощью учащиеся могут самостоятельно анализировать собственные результаты.

Кроме того, цифровые ресурсы открывают широкие возможности для самостоятельной работы: интерактивные энциклопедии, образовательные платформы и развивающие программы позволяют школьникам углублять знания по интересующим темам в индивидуальном темпе. Применение проектной методики и проведение междисциплинарных занятий также становятся более эффективными при поддержке ИКТ, особенно в условиях отхода от традиционной классно-урочной модели. Наконец, отдельные цифровые инструменты помогают развивать когнитивные способности учащихся, такие как память, внимание и логическое мышление.

Учитывая особенности преподавания русского языка и литературы в школе применяются компьютерные технологии в обучении этих предметов по нескольким

направлениям как в урочной, так и во внеурочной деятельности: как банк справочного материала, как средство управления учением обучающегося, динамическое средство условной наглядности, средство организации проблемной ситуации, способствующее исследовательской работе учащихся. Компьютерные технологии способствуют научной организации труда ученика и учителя, самостоятельной исследовательской работе учеников для подготовки к уроку, научно – практическим конференциям, семинарам. Они находят широкое применение в образовательной практике – как в рамках стандартных уроков, так и на факультативных занятиях, в кружках, исследовательской и проектной деятельности, а также при взаимодействии с учащимися через электронную почту и другие цифровые средства связи. Их можно задействовать на всех этапах учебного процесса: начиная с подачи нового материала и заканчивая повторением, закреплением знаний и итоговым контролем усвоенного.

Причём роль компьютера в обучении может быть многогранной. В зависимости от ситуации он способен выступать как виртуальный педагог, как инструмент для выполнения заданий, как объект изучения, как часть учебного взаимодействия, а также как элемент игровой среды, способствующей активному обучению. В функции «учителя» компьютер предоставляет доступ к образовательным материалам, частично заменяя традиционные источники – учебники и устные объяснения преподавателя. Он может выступать в роли мультимедийного наглядного пособия, значительно расширяющего возможности визуального восприятия за счёт использования графики, звука и видеоматериалов. Также компьютер формирует индивидуальное информационное пространство ученика, где возможно как самостоятельное изучение, так и выполнение упражнений, прохождение тренажёров, контроль и самопроверка знаний [2, с .25-27]. Каждый педагог стремится пробудить интерес учащихся к своему предмету, способствовать развитию их познавательной активности и стремлению к саморазвитию. Одной из ключевых задач в образовательном процессе является формирование у обучающихся внутренней мотивации к изучению дисциплины, осознания её значимости, а также устойчивого интереса к познанию.

С этой целью на занятиях активно применяются различные проектные методы. Использование ИКТ требует от учителя внедрения новых педагогических подходов, способствующих активному включению обучающихся в учебный процесс. Недаром Рене Декарт утверждал: «Важно не просто обладать разумом, но и уметь правильно им пользоваться». Интеграция современных цифровых технологий в школьное обучение открывает новые перспективы для совершенствования методик преподавания. При этом необходимо не только разрабатывать инновационные формы работы с мультимедийными средствами, но и совершенствовать уже имеющиеся методы, добиваясь максимальной эффективности их применения.

Тем не менее, важно учитывать, что бездумное полагание исключительно на технологии, без активного участия мышления и личного усилия, может привести к снижению интеллектуальной активности обучающихся. Поэтому задачей педагога является не только контроль за использованием информационно-коммуникационных технологий в учебной деятельности, но и оказание поддержки школьникам в отборе достоверных источников информации и формировании собственной аргументированной точки зрения. Применение информационных технологий позволяет формировать ключевые компетенции учащихся. Помогают решить эти проблемы учебные компьютерные программы по русскому языку и литературе, которых в настоящее время создано достаточно много. Они позволяют повысить

интерес учащихся к предмету, успеваемость и качество знаний, сэкономить время на опрос, дают возможность обучающимся самостоятельно заниматься не только на уроках, но и в домашних условиях, помогают и учителю повысить уровень своих знаний.

На сегодняшний день самостоятельное обучение приобретает всё большую значимость, становясь неотъемлемой частью концепции непрерывного образования. Информационные технологии открывают перед учащимися широкие горизонты для личностного и профессионального роста. Так, онлайн-платформы, предлагающие открытые образовательные курсы – такие как Coursera, Stepik, Khan Academy и другие, – позволяют изучать дисциплины, преподаваемые в ведущих мировых университетах, не выходя из дома. Кроме того, активно развиваются мобильные приложения, ориентированные на развитие конкретных навыков – от изучения иностранных языков до освоения основ программирования и логики проектного мышления.

Особого внимания заслуживают интеллектуальные цифровые инструменты: искусственный интеллект и виртуальные ассистенты сегодня способны не только генерировать тексты или проверять задания, но и рекомендовать обучающие материалы, выстраивая индивидуальные маршруты самообразования в зависимости от уровня и потребностей пользователя. Не менее важную роль играют специализированные онлайн-сообщества и образовательные платформы, где пользователи делятся опытом, обсуждают актуальные темы и помогают друг другу в освоении нового материала.

Следует подчеркнуть, что успех в самообучении в значительной степени определяется степенью цифровой компетентности учащегося, а также его способностью к самодисциплине, осознанному планированию и критическому осмыслению получаемых знаний.

Во всех областях науки и техники применение компьютера стало неотъемлемой частью технического прогресса. Компьютеры дают возможность использовать в учебном процессе уже имеющиеся обучающие системы, создавать на их основе новые собственные программы, внедрять совершенные автоматизированные системы обучения. Учебные материалы должны соответствовать программе, помочь учащимся получить знания, указанные в программе, формы заданий должны служить для формирования и развития речевых навыков, умений на их основе.

На сегодняшний день задача создания эффективных обучающих и контролирующих программ является наиболее проблемной, так как для её решения требуется объединение усилий специалистов по различным отраслям знаний: учителей, программистов, методистов, дизайнеров и других. Компьютер целесообразно использовать в качестве средства эффективного обучения для формирования навыков интенсивного мышления учащихся.

Также в данное время всех волнует проблема повышение грамотности. Орфографическая грамотность – это важнейшее качество письменной речи учащихся; её развитию на уроках русского языка необходимо уделять максимум внимания. Вооружить учащихся прочными орфографическими навыками – одно из важнейших программных требований, выполнение которого при обучении русскому языку требует от учителя больших усилий. В школьной программе последовательно рассматриваются все ключевые разделы русской орфографии: от правил передачи звуков и морфем с помощью букв до норм слитного, дефисного и отдельного написания слов, употребления заглавных и строчных букв, а также переноса слов с одной строки на другую. Современная методика преподавания русского языка исходит из признания

того, что орфографическая грамотность формируется значительно устойчивее, если развивается не изолированно, а в контексте полноценной речевой деятельности. Поэтому одной из приоритетных задач преподавания орфографии в национальной школе становится определение оптимального объема и содержания орфографического материала, который действительно необходимо освоить учащимся. При этом важно учесть, как этот материал связан с другими аспектами языка и с работой по развитию русской речи – как устной, так и письменной.

Особое внимание следует уделять формированию у школьников правильной речи – ведь без грамотного произношения невозможно достичь уверенного владения орфографическими нормами. На практике учащиеся, для которых русский язык не является родным, зачастую сталкиваются с трудностями при усвоении правил. Чтобы повысить результативность обучения, необходимо привлекать современные технические средства – в частности, компьютерные технологии, способные существенно трансформировать методы преподавания. Использование электронных образовательных инструментов открывает возможности для более эффективного и гибкого подхода, особенно в условиях индивидуализации обучения. Однако для этого важно учитывать начальный уровень подготовки каждого ученика, его особенности и потребности.

В современном образовательном процессе крайне важно не просто использовать цифровые технологии, но и делать это осознанно и разумно. Полное упование на технические средства без вовлечения собственных интеллектуальных усилий может привести к снижению уровня критического мышления у обучающихся и формированию пассивного отношения к учебе. Поэтому задача педагога – не только внедрять информационные технологии в урок, но и контролировать их применение, помогая учащимся ориентироваться в потоке информации, выбирать действительно полезные источники и формулировать собственные мысли.

Для того чтобы информационные технологии действительно способствовали улучшению качества образования, необходимо не только решать технические и организационные вопросы, но и активно работать над повышением квалификации учителей. Также важно разрабатывать продуманные методики, которые помогут использовать технологии во благо – без потери образовательной эффективности. При грамотной интеграции цифровых решений обучение становится более насыщенным, увлекательным и доступным для каждого.

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O‘QUVCHILARNING AXLOQIY FAZILATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA OILANING O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o‘quvchilarda axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirishda oilaning o‘rni, ota-onaning namunaliligi, oilaviy muhitning ta’siri hamda maktab va oila

hamkorligi masalalari yoritilgan. Maqolada zamonaviy oilalardagi tarbiyaviy muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha takliflar ham berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: axloqiy fazilatlar, oila, tarbiya, o'quvchi, ota-ona, ma'naviyat, pedagogika, maktab, odob, farzand, hamkorlik, oilaviy muloqot,

„Bizni hamisha o'yantirib keladigan yana bir muhim masala – bu yoshlarimizning odob-axloqi, yurish-turishi, bir so'z bilan aytganda, dunyoqarashi bilan bog'liq. Bugun zamon shiddat bilan o'zgaryapti. Bu o'zgarishlarni hammadan ham ko'proq his etadigan kim – yoshlar. Mayli, yoshlar o'z davrining talablari bilan uyg'un bo'lsin. Lekin ayni paytda o'zligini ham unutmasin. Biz kimmiz, qanday ulug' zotlarning avlodimiz, degan da'vat ularning qalbida doimo aks-sado berib, o'zligiga sodiq qolishga undab tursin. Bunga nimaning hisobidan erishamiz? Tarbiya, tarbiya va faqat tarbiya hisobidan”.¹

Bugungi kunda yosh avlodni komil inson sifatida tarbiyalash har bir oila, maktab va butun jamiyatning eng muhim vazifasidir. O'quvchilarda axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirishda eng birlamchi muhit bu - oila hisoblanadi. Chunki bola dunyoni avvalo oilada, ota-onasi orqali tanlaydi. Oila - bu jamiyatning bir bo'g'inidir, tarbiyaning birinchi maktabi, ota-ona esa uning birinchi ustozidir.

Axloqiy fazilatlar - bu insonning halollik, adolat, sadoqat, mehr-oqibat, hurmat, mas'uliyat, odob kabi ichki sifatlarini ifodalaydigan xulq-atvor me'yorlari majmuasidir. Oddiy so'z bilan aytganda, axloqiy fazilatlar - bu insonni inson qiladigan ichki sifatlar: to'g'rilik, samimiyat, mas'uliyat, sabr, sadoqat, hurmat, adolat, halollik kabi fazilatlar. Shaxsda bu fazilatlar tarbiya, muhit va shaxsiy tajriba orqali shakllanadi.

Pedagog olim A. Umarovning ta'kidlashicha, “axloqiy fazilatlar insonning ijtimoiy me'yorlarga asoslangan, ongli xatti-harakatida namoyon bo'ladigan barqaror sifatlar tizimidir”.²

Oila bolaning eng yaqin va tabiiy tarbiya muhiti hisoblanadi. Farzand dastlab axloqiy me'yorlarni o'z ota-onasining xatti-harakatidan o'rganadi. Agar bola oilasida mehr, hurmat, halollik, sabr kabi qadriyatlarni ko'rsa, u ularni tabiiy ravishda o'zlashtiradi. Ota-onaning bir-biriga mehr bilan munosabatda bo'lishi, kattalarni hurmat qilishi, rostgo'y bo'lishi farzand uchun amaliy namuna bo'ladi. Bolaning axloqiy dunyoqarashi og'zaki nasihatlardan ko'ra, ota-onaning shaxsiy namunasi orqali shakllanadi. Shu jihatdan, qomusiy olim, buyuk bobomiz Abu Ali Ibn Sino o'zining „Tadbir ul - manozil " asarida : “Farzand tarbiyasida avvalo ota-ona o'zini tarbiyalashi zarur. Chunki bola ota-onaning so'ziga emas, amaliy xulqiga taqlid qiladi.”³ - deya ta'kidlaydi.

Farzand ilk tarbiyani oiladan oladi va shu ilk berilgan tarbiya uning hayoti davomida o'z ifodasini topadi. Ota ona farzandining axloqiy fazilatlarini yoshlikdan ularga o'rgatib borishi va bu jihatdan o'zlari namuna bo'lmog'i lozim.

Kattalarga hurmatda bo'lishni o'rgatishi ya'ni bobo va buvilarga, ota-onalarga, aka va opalarga yaxshi munosabatda bo'lish, ulardan hol-ahvol so'rashni o'rgatmoq lozim.

Mehr - shafqatni rivojlantirish va tarbiyalash, misol uchun bolalarni yoshligidan atrofdagilarga mehrlil va yaxshi munosabatda bo'lishga, hayvonlarga mehrlil bo'lishni, ularga ozor bermaslikni o'rgatish.

Bolalarni yoshlikdan mehnatsevarlikga o'rgatish ya'ni ularga yoshligidan turli yumushlarni bajarishga o'rgatish va shu orqali mehnatni qadrlashga o'rgatish.

Bolalarni rostgo'ylikga o'rgatish, hech qachon yolg'on gapirmaslikga o'rgatish, yolg'on hech qachon manfaatli bo'lmasligini ularga yoshligidan uqtirish.

Qo'llab quvvatlovchi muhitni yaratish yani oiladagi barcha a'zolari doimo qo'llab quvvatlash, ularga mehr muhabbatli, doimo yordam berib ularni qo'llash hissini uyg'otish va tarbiyalab borish va bu orqali oiladagi ijodiy muhit va yaqinlik hissini yaratish muhimdir.

Muloqot madaniyatini o'rgatish, bolalarga yoshligidan kattalarga baland ovozda gapirmaslikni, insonlarni oldida o'zini tuta bilishni, gapni bo'lmaslikni va shu kabi qoidalarni o'rgatish va doimo buni ta'kidlab borish farzand tarbiyasida juda muhim.

Tozalik va tartibliqlikni o'rgatish, bolalarga yoshligidan tozalikga rioya qilishlarini o'rgatish, har bir ishda tartibli bo'lishi, tartibli bo'lgan ishda doim unum bo'lishi haqida yoshlarga tushunchalar berish lozim.

Mas'uliyat hissini shakllantirish, bu bilan har bir bola o'ziga yuklatilgan topshiriq va vazifalarni o'z vaqtida bajarishni o'rganadilar bu esa ularda mustaqillilik va mas'uliyat hissini uyg'otadi.

Asosiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish, oilada farzandning axloqiy kompasini tashkil etuvchi: hurmat, halollik, sevgi, mehr tuyg'ulari ularning yanada jipslashuvini taminlaydi.

Axloqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish ya'ni ota onalar frzandlariga savollar berish va o'z fikrlarini ifoda etishga undash orqali axloqiy masalalar yuzasidan tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Farzandlar tarbiyasida axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirishning oiladan keyingi jarayon ta'lim muassasalari roli hisoblanadi

Empatiya ya'ni boshqalarning his-tuyg'ularini tushunish va baham ko'rish va ularning qiyin paytlarida hamdard bo'lish, boshqalarga g'amxo'rlik qilish, mehribonlik ko'rsatish kabi sifatning yoshlikdan o'rgatilishi bolaning axloqiy fazilatlarini mustahkamlaydi.

Farzandlar tarbiyasida axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirishning oiladan keyingi jarayon ta'lim muassasalarining roli hisoblanadi. O'quvchilarda axloqiy fazilatlarni rivojlantirish faqat oilaning vazifasi emas, balki maktab bilan hamkorlikda amalga oshiriladigan uzviy jarayondir. Maktabda o'qituvchi tarbiyaviy soatlar, suhbatlar, sinf tadbirlari orqali axloqiy fazilatlarni mustahkamlasa, oila esa bu fazilatlarni kundalik hayotda qo'llashga o'rgatadi. Masalan, o'qituvchi halollik haqida dars o'tsa, oila esa bolaga shaxsiy hayotda yolg'on gapirmaslikni amalda ko'rsatishi kerak. Shu tarzda ta'lim va tarbiya bir-birini to'ldiradi.

Zamonaviy oilalarda bugungi kunda tarbiyaviy muammolar ko'p hollarda texnologiya, vaqt yetishmasligi, ota-onalarning bandligi yoki qadriyatlardagi o'zgarishlar, oilaviy muloqotning kamayishi kabi holatlar axloqiy tarbiyani susaytiradi. Natijada bolalar e'tibor va mehr yetishmasligidan, odob-axloq normalariga befarq bo'lib qolishlari mumkin. Shu bois, zamonaviy ota-onalar nafaqat moddiy, balki ma'naviy mas'uliyatni ham chuqur his etishlari lozim.

Bunga bir qancha amaliy takliflarni keltirishimiz mumkin:

Ota-onalarning tarbiyaviy savodxonligini oshirish, ota-onalar uchun psixologik va pedagogik seminarlar, "farzand tarbiyasida zamonaviy yondashuvlar" mavzusida treninglar tashkil etish kerak. Masalan, ota-onalar bolaga faqat buyruq bermasdan, tinglash, tushunish va qo'llab-quvvatlash ko'nikmalarini o'rganishlari lozim.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, oila o'quvchilarning axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantirishda eng asosiy tarbiyaviy muhit hisoblanadi. Ota-onaning namunaliligi, mehr-muhabbati, oilaviy muloqot madaniyati bola shaxsini komillikka yo'naltiradi. Maktab esa bu jarayonni ilmiy asosda mustahkamlab, oilaga pedagogik yordam berishi kerak. Shuning uchun, har bir oila o'z farzandining ma'naviy dunyosiga e'tiborli bo'lib, uni halollik, adolat, sadoqat, sabr, hurmat kabi fazilatlar asosida voyaga yetkazishi zarur.

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PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING PRECEDENT PHENOMENA IN LINGUOCULTURAL EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article examines the key principles of teaching precedent phenomena as an essential component of linguocultural education. It highlights the importance of integrating linguistic, cultural, and cognitive approaches to develop students' intercultural competence. The study emphasizes contextualization, cultural analogy, and communicative relevance as core principles for effective instruction. Teaching strategies such as discourse analysis, cultural comparison, and interactive learning help students recognize and interpret culturally marked units, enhancing their linguistic awareness and cultural literacy in authentic communication.

Keywords: precedent phenomena, linguocultural education, intercultural competence, teaching principles.

Main text. In modern linguocultural education, the study of precedent phenomena has gained particular importance as a means of shaping intercultural awareness and communicative competence. Precedent phenomena—well-known texts, names, and situations reflecting national culture—serve as cognitive keys to understanding the mentality and values of a linguistic community. However, their effective teaching requires clear methodological principles that combine linguistic, cultural, and pragmatic dimensions. This paper focuses on identifying and systematizing the basic principles of teaching precedent phenomena in the process of foreign language instruction, emphasizing their role in forming learners' cultural literacy and discourse competence.

The concept of precedent phenomena was first defined by Y.N. Karaulov as culturally and linguistically marked units shared by a community [2, p.216]. Later, V.V. Krasnykh emphasized their cognitive and communicative functions in intercultural discourse [3, p.47]. According to M.V. Gudkov, precedent phenomena serve as carriers of cultural memory and national identity [1, p.138]. These scholars highlight that teaching such units requires a linguocultural approach combining language, cognition, and culture. Their works provide the theoretical basis for developing methodological principles that help learners interpret and use precedent phenomena effectively in foreign language communication.

The study integrates linguistic, cultural, and cognitive approaches to teaching precedent phenomena in linguocultural education. Descriptive, analytical, and comparative methods were used to examine how learners interpret and apply precedent units in authentic contexts. Classroom observations and small-scale teaching experiments were conducted with English-major students at National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan. Students analyzed and discussed examples such as *“Achilles’ heel,” “Big Brother,” “To open Pandora’s box”*—representing English cultural precedents. During instruction, activities included comparative discourse analysis, role-play dialogues, and contextual translation tasks. Learners were encouraged to interpret precedent expressions within historical and literary frameworks. This methodology enabled students to connect linguistic forms with cultural meanings, reflecting both national and universal cognitive patterns. The comparative analysis also helped reveal

cross-cultural similarities, enhancing the students' awareness of intercultural communicative norms and metaphorical thinking.

The results showed that contextualized and comparative teaching of precedent phenomena significantly improved learners' cultural and pragmatic comprehension. When discussing "*Achilles' heel*," students correctly identified it as "a weak point" after learning its mythological origin, and linked it with the Uzbek concept "*zaif nuqta*". Similarly, analyzing "*Pandora's box*" alongside "*Ochilmagan sandiq*" helped students grasp how myths function as sources of moral and cultural symbolism.

Students demonstrated stronger recall and usage when tasks involved visual aids (images from Greek mythology, Uzbek epics) and discourse-based exercises such as short dialogues ("This policy became the government's Achilles' heel"). Teachers reported increased motivation and creativity among learners during interactive sessions. However, comprehension difficulties persisted when precedent units were highly culture-bound ("*Big Brother*," "*Waterloo*"), suggesting the need for pre-teaching of cultural contexts. Overall, the findings confirm that systematic instruction based on contextualization, analogy, and cultural explanation fosters deeper understanding of precedent phenomena as a means of intercultural communication.

The study confirms that teaching precedent phenomena plays a vital role in developing students' linguocultural and intercultural competence. Effective instruction requires adherence to the principles of contextualization, cultural analogy, and communicative relevance. By integrating linguistic, cognitive, and cultural approaches, educators can help learners decode and use precedent units such as "*Achilles' heel*" or "*Alpomish*" meaningfully in communication. The findings suggest that culturally grounded explanations and comparative activities significantly improve comprehension and motivation. Consequently, systematic inclusion of precedent phenomena in language curricula enhances not only linguistic proficiency but also students' ability to understand and reflect the cultural worldview of the target language.

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ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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Аннотация. Художественный текст играет особую роль в обучении русскому языку как иностранному. Он позволяет соединить языковую и культурную стороны обучения, сделать процесс изучения более живым и осмысленным. Практический опыт показывает, что включение литературных текстов в систему занятий по РКИ способствует повышению мотивации и коммуникативной активности учащихся.

Ключевые слова: художественный текст; дидактический потенциал; русский язык как иностранный; методика обучения; билингвальная среда.

Современное обучение русскому языку как иностранному требует не только знания грамматики и лексики, но и глубокого понимания культурного контекста, в котором существует язык. Одним из самых эффективных средств такого погружения является художественный текст. Через литературу учащиеся получают возможность увидеть язык «в действии», почувствовать его образность, эмоциональную окраску и национально-культурные особенности [2, с. 63].

Особенно это важно в билингвальной среде, где изучение русского языка происходит параллельно с родным. Для иностранных студентов художественные произведения становятся не просто материалом для чтения, а мостом между двумя культурами [3, с. 82]. Работа с текстом позволяет им осознаннее воспринимать смысловую структуру языка, замечать различия в способах выражения мыслей и чувств, а также развивать навыки интерпретации и собственного речевого творчества.

Кроме того, художественный текст обладает мощным дидактическим потенциалом. Он способствует формированию всех видов речевой деятельности - чтения, аудирования, говорения и письма - и одновременно развивает критическое мышление, воображение и эмоциональную отзывчивость. Использование таких текстов на уроках РКИ делает процесс обучения более мотивирующим и способствует более прочному усвоению языкового материала [4, с. 118].

Теоретические основы исследования

«Художественный текст» традиционно занимает особое место в системе обучения иностранным языкам. Он является не только источником языкового материала, но и формой культурного опыта народа, на языке которого создан. В методике преподавания РКИ художественный текст рассматривается как универсальное средство, позволяющее сочетать обучение языку и приобщение к русской культуре.

Исследователи отмечают, что художественный текст выполняет сразу несколько функций: познавательную, воспитательную, коммуникативную и эстетическую. Он формирует у учащихся представление о национальных ценностях, исторических реалиях и менталитете русского народа. Кроме того, в отличие от учебных текстов, художественное произведение воздействует на эмоциональную сферу обучающихся, что способствует лучшему запоминанию и усвоению языкового материала.

Дидактический потенциал художественного текста проявляется в том, что он позволяет решать сразу несколько задач обучения:

- развивать навыки чтения и понимания текста;
- обогащать активный словарный запас;
- закреплять грамматические структуры в естественном контексте;

- формировать навыки устной и письменной речи;
- развивать межкультурную компетенцию.

Художественный текст обладает значительным дидактическим потенциалом в обучении русскому языку как иностранному. Он выступает не только как источник языкового материала, но и как средство формирования речевой, социокультурной и эмоционально-ценностной компетенции. Через обращение к литературе обучающиеся осваивают не только грамматические структуры и лексику, но и приобщаются к духовному опыту народа, к его культурным и нравственным традициям.

Анализ практических результатов показывает, что систематическое использование художественного текста делает процесс обучения более содержательным и мотивирующим. Работа с произведениями литературы способствует развитию самостоятельности, творческого мышления и эстетического вкуса, а также формирует устойчивый интерес к русскому языку как к средству познания иной культуры.

Таким образом, включение художественного текста в методическую систему преподавания русского языка как иностранного является важным условием успешного формирования языковой личности обучающегося и создания билингвальной образовательной среды, способствующей диалогу культур.

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CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS AS AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN LANGUAGE UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation. The digitalization of higher education has rendered traditional, form-focused language teaching obsolete, as it fails to address pragmatic and intercultural dimensions of communication. This article argues that contrastive analysis, when reconceptualized as a digitally supported pedagogical strategy, functions as an innovative approach to developing intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in language universities. In contrast to grammar-translation methods, it reveals ethnocultural norms of communicative behavior and prevents pragmatic failure in real interaction. Integrated with platforms such as Padlet, Edpuzzle, YouTube corpora, and AI scenario modeling, contrastive analysis becomes a scalable and replicable tool that enables students to detect, interpret, and adapt to cross-cultural variation in speech acts and politeness strategies. The paper justifies its relevance for Uzbekistan's university classrooms by presenting contrastive analysis as an

implementable and policy-aligned innovation that meets the demands of contemporary academic and professional mobility.

Keywords: contrastive analysis, intercultural communicative competence, digital pedagogy, pragmatic failure, speech acts, ethnocultural communicative behavior, higher education, innovation.

Intercultural miscommunication in English-medium academic and professional interactions rarely stems from grammatical error; it is overwhelmingly triggered by pragmatic transfer - the unconscious import of native ethnocultural norms into a foreign-language context. A learner may construct a syntactically correct utterance and still fail communicatively because the illocutionary force they intend is decoded differently by interlocutors from other cultures. Such failures are not random deviations but patterned outcomes of culturally encoded communicative behavior. Therefore, any method that claims relevance for 21st-century language education must treat intercultural pragmatics not as an optional add-on but as the core risk domain demanding systematic pedagogical intervention [5, p.242].

Contrastive analysis, reconceived not as a structuralist relic but as a competence-building strategy, directly targets this risk by making cultural scripts analytically visible and behaviorally negotiable. The original contrastive hypothesis framed in the mid-20th century focused on predicting formal interference in syntax and phonology [7, p.33], but the contemporary threat in globalized communication originates not in forms but in pragmatic regimes - refusals, apologies, compliments, offers, greetings - whose cultural realization diverges sharply across ethnolinguistic groups [2, p.114; 3, p.89]. When students perform a refusal in English using direct structures inherited from Russian or Uzbek norms, they commit a pragmatic infelicity even when grammatically flawless [10, p.57; 2, p.114]. Conversely, when they formulate an English apology with Russian brevity or Uzbek ritualization, they risk being perceived as insincere or incomplete despite lexical correctness [3, p.89; 8, p.67].

The claim that contrastive analysis is “not innovative” collapses once innovation is defined functionally rather than chronologically. A method is “innovative” in higher education when it (1) prevents the dominant failure mode; (2) produces operational competence rather than declarative knowledge; and (3) scales under digital conditions. Contrastive analysis in its re-engineered pedagogical form satisfies all three conditions. First, it directly immunizes learners against pragmatic failure by pre-exposing them to intercultural divergence before real-world breakdown occurs. Second, it transforms recognition of difference into strategic behavioral adaptability - the essence of intercultural communicative competence. Third, digital mediation (Padlet maps, Edpuzzle pauses, YouTube corpora, AI interlocutors) converts contrastive analysis from a descriptive narrative into a replicable training architecture at classroom scale [6, p.53; 9, p.41].

Digitalization is not an aesthetic upgrade but a structural enabler: without large samples of authentic intercultural discourse, contrastive analysis would remain abstract and teacher-declared rather than empirically verifiable [6, p.53]. Streaming platforms, political speeches, podcasts, sitcom transcripts, interview archives, and AI chatbots supply living material in which learners can detect contrasts in stance, mitigation, address forms, and ritual formulas without relying on intuition or hearsay. This shift - from teacher-imposed contrast to learner-discovered contrast - is what converts contrastive analysis from a linguistic commentary into a competence technology. Learners cease being passive recipients of cultural facts and become analysts of actionable difference.

To dismiss contrastive analysis as “old” because it appeared in the 1950s is to commit a chronological fallacy. A method’s birth date is irrelevant; its capacity to solve unsolved

present problems is decisive [5, p.242]. In the digital, intercultural, competence-based regime of higher education, contrastive analysis is innovative not by invention but by necessity. It neutralizes the precise failure mechanism (pragmatic misalignment), uses digital affordances unavailable to earlier generations, and produces transferable behavioral outcomes instead of ornamental cultural commentary. No rival method currently satisfies these conditions with equal parsimony or replicability.

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**ZAMONAVIY ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA ILMIY-NAZARIY
TADQIQOTLARNING DOLZARB MASALALARI**

**ОБЩНОСТЬ И СПЕЦИФИКА В ЭТИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЯХ
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПРОСВЕТИТЕЛЕЙ XX ВЕКА АБДУРАХМАНА ТАШКАНДИ
И АБДУЛЛЫ АВЛОНИ**

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Аннотация. Мы знаем, что каждое общество воспитывает того человека, которого считает нужным. И исходя из собственных факторов и тенденций развития, она предъявляет к ней религиозно-нравственные, профессионально-правовые и ряд других требований. Из работ Абдурахмана Ташканди и Абдуллы Авлони мы видим, что моральные нормы, необходимые для формирования нравственных качеств при воспитании молодого поколения, находятся в систематизированном виде.

Ключевые слова: Тело, душа, хорошие и плохие качества, моральные качества, «Меъёр уль-Ахлак», «Туркий гулистан ёхуд ахлок», альтернативные добродетели, сиротол мустахим (правильный путь).

Богатое наследие, оставленное Абдурахманом Ташканди и Абдуллою Авлони, напрямую считается духовным достоянием нашего народа. Нам приятно узнать больше о том, что наши просвещенные предки, которые были национальными лидерами такого высокого уровня в тот сложный колониальный период, самоотверженно творили, своей практической деятельностью вносили свой вклад в повышение просвещения нации, и наслаждаются полнотой своих произведений. только честь независимости позволила нам быть такими.

В интерпретации работ Абдурахмана Ташканди и Абдуллы Авлони по науке этики проанализируем их общие и частные аспекты.

Ташканди говорит: «Человек состоит из двух вещей: первая – это тело, а вторая – душа, которую еще называют вожделием. Тело можно увидеть глазами и ощутить руками, но душу нельзя увидеть с помощью внешних органов. Это можно познать с помощью интеллекта и басират. Вот почему внешний образ человека называется нацией, а внутренний образ – характером»¹.

По словам Авлони, «Человек сложен двумя вещами. Одно - тело, другое - душа. Тело видит всё своими глазами. Но это отделяет хорошее от плохого и белое от черного. И тело, и душа имеют образ либо хороший, либо плохой. Изображение трупа – это что-то известное каждому, что всегда видно. Но образ души есть нечто такое, что нельзя увидеть глазом и можно измерить разумом, что и называется поведением»².

Оба современных просветителя делят поведение, лежащее в основе морали, на два типа: хорошее поведение и плохое поведение.

По определению Ташканди: «добродетели, возникающие в результате честного и справедливого обращения с людьми, являются добродетелями или хорошими

¹ ۱۹۱۲, تاشکند، غلام حسن آرفجانوف متبعی. عبدالرحمان سیاح تاشکندی – معیار الاخلاق. تاشکند، ۱۹۱۲ گ. – С. 27-28.

² Абдулла Авлони. Туркий гулистан ёхуд ахлок. Т.: 2004. –С. 3.

манерами, а пороки, возникающие из-за небрежности и лени в совершении этих дел, являются пороками или плохими манерами»³.

Авлони говорит: «Учёные-этики делят человеческое поведение на две части: если душа дисциплинирована и привыкает совершать добрые дела, то это описание добра, и «хорошее поведение», если она вырастает без тренировки и приобретает привычку совершать плохие поступки. вещи, это зло. Это описание и оно называется «плохим поведением»⁴.

По Авлони, «Хорошие манеры: использовать одну часть для себя и одну часть друг против друга, хорошие манеры, которые необходимы: вера, религиозность, ислам, благодать, энтузиазм, смирение, довольство, энтузиазм, знания, терпение, знания, дисциплина», , самоуважение, совесть, любовь к Родине, правдивость, пример, целомудрие, скромность, понимание и ум, безопасный язык, экономность, достоинство, опасность и надежда, послушание, справедливость, доброжелательность, нравственность, верность, любовь и прощение»⁵.

У Тошканди же несколько иной подход к хорошим манерам или моральным качествам. Он говорит: «Всевышний Аллах создал человеческую душу из трёх сил: интеллектуальной силы (нафси мут'маинна или нафси малаки), силы гнева (нафси лоувума) и сексуальной силы (нафси аммара или нафси бахими)»⁶. В основе этого «нравственные качества осложняются еще и этими качествами: мудростью, мужеством и целомудрием. Некоторые судьи разделили моральные добродетели на 4 части и решили, что четвертая - справедливость»⁷.

Здесь обратим внимание на определения, данные Ташканди в «Меяр уль-Ахлак» и «Туркий Гулистан Яхуд Ахлак» Авлони понятиям мужества, целомудрия и справедливости, которые можно найти в обоих вышеперечисленных моральных качествах.

В Тошканди к вышесказанному подходят так: «Мужество – это причина, по которой человек проявляет храбрость, не рискуя собой. Они борются с ними, несмотря на невзгоды и трудности. Он не впускает страх в свое сердце. Основа мужества - сохранять энергию гнева в умеренных количествах. Целомудрие – это состояние удовлетворения вследствие отречения души от преходящих похотей. Основой целомудрия является умеренность сексуальной энергии.

Справедливость – это правдивость и правильность в действиях, а значит расставить все на свои места. Основой справедливости является умеренность вышеуказанных сил»⁸.

В Авлони подход меняется: «Кураж – смелый и сердечный человек. Смелый человек – это смелый и отважный человек, который ничего не боится. Подобно тому, как противоположностью усилий и энтузиазма является лень и лень, противоположностью смелости является трусость»⁹.

³ ۱۹۱۲، تاشکند، عبد الرحمان سياح تاشکندی – معيار الاخلاق. غلام حسن آرفجانوف متبعی. تاشکند، ۱۹۱۲ (Абдурахман Сайёх Ташканди-Меяр ул-Ахлак. Типография Гулама Хасана Оруфджанова. Ташкент, 1912 г.) – С. 20.

⁴ Абдулла Авлони. Туркий гулистан йохуд ахлоқ. Т.: 2004. –С. 4.

⁵ Абдулла Авлони. Туркий гулистан йохуд ахлоқ. Т.: 2004. –С. 10.

⁶ ۱۹۱۲، تاشکند، عبد الرحمان سياح تاشکندی – معيار الاخلاق. غلام حسن آرفجانوف متبعی. تاشکند، ۱۹۱۲ (Абдурахман Сайёх Ташканди-Меяр ул-Ахлак. Типография Гулама Хасана Оруфджанова. Ташкент, 1912 г.) – С. 30.

⁷ Та работа. -С. 35.

⁸ ۱۹۱۲، تاشکند، عبد الرحمان سياح تاشکندی – معيار الاخلاق. غلام حسن آرفجانوف متبعی. تاشکند، ۱۹۱۲ (Абдурахман Сайёх Ташканди-Меяр ул-Ахлак. Типография Гулама Хасана Оруфджанова. Ташкент, 1912 г.) – С. 85.

⁹ Абдулла Авлони. Туркий гулистан йохуд ахлоқ. Т.: 2004. –С. 17.

«Целомудрие означает сохранение нашей души от греха и безнравственности. Только наше целомудрие защищает нас от греха и масията, защищает от нечистоты. Человек нравственный и целомудренный должен беречь свое сердце и совесть и хранить свой язык от плохих слов, таких как ложь, сплетни, клевета и клевета»¹⁰.

«Справедливость означает уважение собственности и чести других. Справедливость - это агент хороших манер, альтернатива тирании. Справедливые и доброжелательные люди не дают другим работу, которой они не заслуживают. Человек может выполнить долг справедливости и гуманности, не только воздерживаясь от плохих поступков, но и исправляя ошибки и недостатки своих сверстников и стремясь на добрый путь» .

Подводя итог, можно сказать, что Абдурахман Ташканди и Абдулла Авлони, современные интеллектуалы национального возрождения XX века, написали и опубликовали свои произведения по просьбе нескольких учителей. Из-за отсутствия в школах Туркестана совершенной книги «Этика», написанной на их диалекте, им было хорошо известно, что они жаждут и нуждаются в подобных произведениях и что они находятся среди учителей и интеллигентов.

Заслуга этих людей в том, что просвещенные педагоги не оставили эти произведения без похвал, а посмотрели на их работы и использовали их последующие труды в системе образования, несмотря на их недостатки.

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ХОДЖА НАСРЕДДИН – В ФОЛЬКЛОРЕ МНОГИХ НАРОДОВ ВОСТОКА

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется, творчество современного русского писателя таджикского происхождения Тимура Зульфикарова и образ Ходжи Насреддина – народного мудреца и остролова в фольклоре многих народов Ближнего и Среднего Востока, Средней Азии. Образ Ходжи Насреддина занимает почетное место в творчестве Тимура Зульфикарова и творенья Зульфикарова – это Пирамиды Духа, Поэзии, Мудрости, Человеколюбия....

¹⁰ Та работа. -С. 30.

Ключевые слова: Тимур Зульфикаров, поэт, прозаик, драматург, Нобелевская премия, фольклор, Ходжа Насреддин, великий мудрец, Таджикистан.

annotation: This article analyzes the work of the modern Russian writer of Tajik origin Timur Zulfikarov and the image Khoja Nasreddin - a folk sage and wit in the folklore of many peoples of the Near and Middle East, Central Asia. The image of Khoja Nasreddin occupies an honorable place in the work of Timur Zulfikarov and Zulfikarov's creations are the Pyramids of the Spirit, Poetry, Wisdom, Philanthropy....

Key words: Timur Zulfikarov, poet, prose writer, playwright, Nobel Prize, folklore, Khoja Nasreddin, great sage, Tajikistan.

Его называют самым религиозным и самым языческим, самым христианским и самым мусульманским. Самым буддийским и самым суфийским. Самым русским и самым таджикским. Самым земным и мистическим. Самым трагическим и сатирическим. И, наконец, самым эротическим и аскетическим.

Т. Успенский

Тимур Зульфикаров - явление в современной российской литературе удивительное. Тимур Зульфикаров поэт, прозаик и драматург, создатель необычного литературного стиля. Он пишет и издает книги высокого поэтического и философского наполнения, которые находят признание у широкого круга ценителей русской словесности как в России, так и зарубежом. Его произведения переведены на 12 языков мира, по ним снято более 20 художественных и документальных фильмов.

Известный поэт Тимур Зульфикаров в 1991 году был выдвинут на соискание Нобелевской премии. В 1993 году за роман «Земные и небесные странствия поэта» получил английскую премию «Коллетс» за лучший европейский роман года. В 2004 году за книгу легенд «Золотые притчи Ходжи Насреддина», «Алмазы мудрости в золотом песке эротики» Тимур Зульфикаров был награжден литературной премией «Ясная Поляна» в номинации «Выдающееся художественное произведение русской литературы». [1, 86]

Наиболее ярко талант писателя проявился в произведениях, посвященных Ходже Насреддину - любимому герою Тимура Зульфикарова. Нарушая «границы» поэзии и прозы, используя яркие и неожиданные художественные образы, традиции всех культурных веков, Тимур Зульфикаров дает тонкое поэтическое толкование истории и реальности, проникая в пласты малых и великих событий, осмысливая проблемы Бытия и простой человеческой жизни от рождения до смерти.

Ходжа Насреддин – образ народного мудреца и остролова в фольклоре многих народов Ближнего и Среднего Востока, Средней Азии (у турок – Ходжа Насреддин и Бу Адам, у узбеков и таджиков – Афанди или Насреддин Ходжа, у иранцев – Мулла, у азербайджанцев – Молла Насреддин). Известен также казанским и крымским татарам, народам Кавказа и Восточной Европы (румынам, сербам) и др. Считают, что историческим прототипом Ходжи Насреддина был некий Имам (мусульманское духовное лицо) родом из Сиврихисара в Турции, по другим сведениям, - из деревни Хорто близ этого города, он увлекся суфизмом, оставил службу и переселился в Акшехир, где умер в 1285 году. На Востоке давно уже был известен образ балагура остролова тешившего правителей. Анекдоты об остроловах арабского средневековья Бахлуне и Джухе проникли в Турцию в 11-12 вв., после принятия ислама и прихода

тюрков-сельджиков. В 14-15 вв. эти анекдоты уже приписывались Ходже Насреддину. В Казахстане с Ходжой Насреддином слился образ шутника Алдара Косе, в Туркмении многие анекдоты связаны с личностью поэта-сатирика Кемине, в Таджикистане – с поэтом Мушфики. [2,120]

Образ Ходжи Насреддина занимает почетное место в творчестве Тимура Зульфикарова. В 2009 году в Москве вышло полное собрание сочинений Тимура Зульфикарова в семи томах. Почти в каждой книге есть повести, рассказы и притчи о Ходже Насреддине. Например, в первом томе «Первая любовь Ходжи Насреддина», во втором томе «Отрочество Ходжи Насреддина», «Ходжи Насреддин и Ходжи Зульфикар», «Последняя встреча с Ходжа Насреддином», в третьем томе «Возвращение Ходжа Насреддина», «Золотые притчи Ходжа Насреддина», в четвертом томе «Ходжа Насреддин», в пятом томе поэма «Туман», в шестом томе «Ходжа Насреддин и Ходжа Зульфикар», «Ходжа Насреддин и завод», «Ходжа Насреддин, Рокфеллер и Золотой Осел», «Письмо Ходжа Насреддина к Президентам Ельцину и Клинтону» и другие.

В поэме «Смерть Ходжи Насреддина» говорится о том, как Ходжа Насреддин устал от многих народов и любви всех людей и хочет умереть в одиночестве, уйти в вечную Дорогу. Он представляет себе, что на этой Дороге встретит свою мать и отца, которая ведет их в Рай. И тут он услышал крик старого утопающего человека и Ходжа бросился к реке и вытащил старика. Тогда Ходжа пошел в глухие горы, где нет людей, а были дикие пещеры и жили звери. Мудрец хотел умереть здесь и та Дорога Усопших явилась ему. И тут ждала его мать и протягивала к нему руку. Но тут появился охотник с ружьём и не дал ему умереть. И он сказал «Не покидай нас великий мудрец! Не уноси с земли несчастных вольную весёлую вечную Мудрость Твою!» Охотник пригласил на свадьбу-туй своей дочери. Тогда мудрец вздохнул, и пошел на свадьбу и ублажал горцев. Горцы ликовали, что великий Мудрец посетил их тихую как родник, в горах свадьбу.

Мудрец ушел в Анзобские горы, лег на снег и хотел умереть. И тут увидел Три Пророка Будда Блаженный, Иисус Христос Смиранный Божественный и Мухаммад Воитель Священный.

Пророк Будда сказал, что хочешь смерти, а я дам тебе вечность. Любовь тленна, жизнь тленна, смерть тленна, Нирвана вечна. Иисус Христос сказал: «Я принес тебе Крест Спасенья, Крест Вечности...»

Святой Мухаммад сказал огненно: «...И меч – это самый краткий путь в Рай...». [3,13]

В четвертый раз, когда Ходжа Насреддин собрался умереть, та Дорога опять появилась ему. Опять мать ждала его на тропинке у горного водопада. Она улыбалась ему необъятно, непостижимо... И от неё струилась такая любовь, который не было у всех Пророков на земле. И тогда Ходжа зарыдал. Тут Ходжа услышал птичий свист, и открыл свои глаза, и земная радость наполнила его.

Ни что в мире не сравнимо с материнской любовью, слова матери лучше всех слов Пророков, материнская улыбка это свет, солнце жизни, которая вернет нас к вечной жизни.

В «Притче о Золотом Автобусе» говорится о том, что как в этом мире все народы стали похожи друг на друга, все стали одевать одинаковые одежды, и стали говорить на одном английском языке. И этот мир стал похож на автобус, который ведет всех народов в ад.

В притче «Ах, Азия – необъятная чайхана» рассказывается о нашей Родине Таджикистан, как жизнь в нем протекает медленно, как «молодой государственный Корабль Таджикистана сладко плывет в океане бедняков», среди народов мира.

Мудрец сказал: «Народы это мысли Бога. Кто против мыслей Бога? ...Кто?.. А это шайтан...». Политики говорят, что в мире много партий... Но в мире есть только две партии – партия Бога и партия сатаны. Дай Бог, что родная Азия, родной Таджикистан жил и процветал среди народов мира и всевозможных партий.

Ходжа Насреддин - хранитель небесной и земной мудрости. Небесный орёл и тяжкий муравей земли. И это не одесский скоропалительный, скоротечный Острослов, а печальный мудрец, брат царя Соломона." Смех- это молоко, мудрость - мясо. Корова много раз дает молоко, но лишь однажды - мясо"... - говорит Насреддин. Это Омар Хайям и Мушфики, царь Бахрам-Гур Сасанид и божественный художник, мастер павлиньего хвоста, Камолиддин Бехзад. Это собрат и легенда-фантазия-промысел одинокого нашего поэта - дервиш Ходжа Зульфикар Девона, которого Поэт сотворил в одиночестве, и тот вдруг ожил и самородно, самостийно пошел по пыльным азиатским дорогам и теперь бродит там, и изрекает притчи, и стихи независимо от того, кто родил его. [4,17]

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ALISHER NAVOIY IJODINING JAHON ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIGIDAGI O‘RNI VA “SADDI ISKANDARIY” DOSTONINING TALQINI

Pardayeva Iroda
dotsent

Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti

Annotatsiya Mazkur maqolada Alisher Navoiy ijodiy merosining jahon adabiyotshunoslik maktablarida o‘rganilishi, xususan, “Xamsa” turkumiga kiruvchi “Saddi Iskandariy” dostonining badiiy-falsafiy, tarixiy va estetik mohiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida Navoiy asarlariga doir xalqaro ilmiy izlanishlar yo‘nalishlari, xorijiy va mahalliy olimlar tadqiqotlari o‘rganilib, ularning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari solishtirildi. Maqolada shuningdek, “Saddi Iskandariy” dostonidagi hukmdor shaxsiyati, siyosiy-falsafiy g‘oya va axloqiy qadriyatlarining badiiy ifodasi jahon adabiyotshunosligi nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil etildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Alisher Navoiy, “Saddi Iskandariy”, “Xamsa”, adabiyotshunoslik, Navoiyshunoslik, Iskandar obrazi, falsafiy talqin, Sharq va G‘arb, tasavvuf, siyosiy-axloqiy poetika.

Alisher Navoiy (1441–1501) - o‘zbek mumtoz adabiyotining eng yirik namoyandasi, Sharq uyg‘onish davri tafakkurining timsolidir. Uning ijodiy merosi, ayniqsa “Xamsa” turkumiga kiruvchi “Saddi Iskandariy” dostoni, o‘z davri madaniy-ma’naviy hayotining

yuksak bosqichini ifodalaydi. Shoir nafaqat san'atkor sifatida, balki faylasuf, mutafakkir va davlat arbobi darajasida ham jahon adabiyotida o'z izini qoldirgan.

Bugungi kunda Navoiy merosi turli ilmiy maktablar tomonidan falsafiy, tarixiy, siyosiy, estetik va matnshunoslik jihatidan o'rganilmoqda. Xususan, "Saddi Iskandariy" dostoni Sharq va G'arb adabiy tafakkuri tutashgan nuqtada tahlil etilmoqda. Ushbu asarda tarixiy shaxs - Iskandar obrazining badiiy-falsafiy talqini, adolat, ilm va ma'rifat g'oyalari, hukmdor shaxsiyatining ma'naviy mezonlari yoritiladi.

Navoiy ijodining xalqaro miqyosdagi tadqiqi XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmidan boshlangan bo'lib, bugungi kunda bu yo'nalish qator yetakchi ilmiy markazlarda izchil davom etmoqda. Tehron universiteti (Eron), Balx davlat universiteti (Afg'oniston), Oxford University, Yale University, University of Washington Press, Georgetown University (AQSh), Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi, Ankara Üniversitesi (Turkiya), Rossiya Fanlar akademiyasi Sharqshunoslik instituti (Moskva), Qozon davlat universiteti, Qozoq milliy universiteti, Ozarbayjon Fanlar akademiyasi qo'lyozmalar instituti, Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat o'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti, Samarqand davlat universiteti, Toshkent davlat sharqshunoslik universiteti, O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi va boshqa ilmiy markazlarda bu borada ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda.

Bu izlanishlar Navoiy asarlarining matnshunoslik, poetika, falsafa, tasavvuf, ijtimoiy-falsafiy tafakkur kabi jihatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Masalan, Süleyman Demirel Universiteti va Ankara Universiteti olimlari tomonidan Navoiy asarlarining estetik tuzilmasi, badiiy obrazlar tizimi va tasavvufiy tafakkur manbalari bo'yicha monografiyalar yaratildi. Humboldt University of Berlin va New York University tadqiqotchilari esa Navoiy matnlarining tekstologik xususiyatlarini, qo'lyozmalar tarixini va matnlar tahririni o'rganish bo'yicha yangi metodologik yo'nalishlarni ishlab chiqdilar.

"Saddi Iskandariy" - Navoiyning "Xamsa"sini yakunlovchi asar bo'lib, unda adolatli hukmdor obrazining yaratilishi markaziy o'rinni egallaydi. Navoiy bu asarda tarixiy shaxs Iskandar (Aleksandr Makedonskiy) siymosini yangicha falsafiy ruhda talqin etadi. Shoir uni faqat g'olib sarkarda emas, balki ilm, adolat va tafakkur homiysi, ma'naviy kamolotga intiluvchi inson sifatida gavdalantiradi.

Bu jihatdan doston Nizomiy Ganjaviy va Amir Xusrav Dehlaviyning "Iskandarnoma" an'analarini davom ettirgan bo'lsa-da, Navoiyning talqinida Iskandar obrazi tasavvufiy-falsafiy ma'nolar bilan boyitilgan. U Navoiy tafakkurida adolatli podshoh timsoli sifatida ideal davlat va hukmdor konsepsiyasini ifodalaydi.

Shu bois "Saddi Iskandariy" dostoni ko'plab xorijiy tadqiqotchilar - E. G. Browne, A. J. Arberry, Annemarie Schimmel, P. Chelkowski, Yan Ripka tomonidan Sharq falsafasining universal modeli sifatida o'rganilgan. Ular Navoiyni Sharq adabiy an'analari bilan bir qatorda G'arb gumanistik tafakkuriga yaqinlashtirgan ijodkor sifatida baholaganlar.

Bugungi kunda Navoiyshunoslik quyidagi asosiy ilmiy yo'nalishlar bo'yicha rivojlanmoqda:

1. Qo'lyozma manbalar va matn tarixi: Navoiy asarlarining asl nusxalari, ularning tarixiy tahrir va nashr jarayonlari o'rganilmoqda.
2. Poetika va stilistika: "Xamsa"dagi badiiy vositalar tizimi, metaforik struktura, obrazlar dinamikasi tahlil qilinmoqda.
3. Tasavvuf falsafasi: "Saddi Iskandariy"dagi ruhiy kamolot, adolat, ilohiy nur va ma'rifat konsepsiyasi izchil tadqiq etilmoqda.
4. Tarixiy-adabiy kontekst: Iskandar obrazi orqali Amir Temur davri siyosiy-falsafiy g'oyalari bilan bog'lanish masalasi o'rganilmoqda.
5. Qiyosiy-tarixiy tahlil: Navoiyning "Xamsa"si Ganjaviy, Dehlaviy, Jomiy, Firdavsiy asarlari bilan qiyosiy o'rganilmoqda.

Bu yo‘nalishlar natijasida Navoiy ijodi zamonaviy adabiyotshunoslikning tekstologiya, falsafa, tarixiy poetika, madaniyatshunoslik va qiyosiy adabiyot kabi fanlari bilan uzviy aloqada o‘rganilmoqda.

Rus sharqshunosligida V. Bartold, A. Krimskiy, E. Bertels, A. Kononov, A. Semyonov, M. Salye, A. Yakubovskiy singari olimlar Navoiyning adabiy maktab sifatidagi o‘rnini aniqlashda katta hissa qo‘shgan. Ayniqsa, E. Bertelsning “Navoiy i ego mesto v istorii persidsko-tadjikskoy literatury” asari Navoiy ijodining G‘arbda tanilishiga sabab bo‘lgan.

O‘zbek adabiyotshunosligida esa A. Fitrat, H. Homidiy, P. Shamsiyev, O. Sharafiddinov, N. Mallayev, A. Hayitmetov, N. Komilov, S. G‘aniyeva, Sh. Sirojiddinov, R. Vohidov, E. Ochilov, L. Zohidov kabi olimlarning izlanishlari Navoiy asarlari poetikasining milliy adabiy jarayondagi ahamiyatini belgilab berdi.

Ularning tadqiqotlarida Navoiy “Saddi Iskandariy” dostonining falsafiy qatlamlari, adolat konsepsiyasi, davlat boshqaruvi va hukmdor shaxsiyati haqidagi fikrlari chuqur yoritilgan.

Alisher Navoiy ijodi, xususan “Saddi Iskandariy” dostoni jahon adabiyotida Sharq tafakkurining gumanistik konsepsiyasini ifoda etuvchi bebaho manbadir. Unda hukmdor shaxsining ma‘naviy fazilatlari, ilm va adolatning ijtimoiy asoslari, insonparvarlik tamoyillari badiiy-falsafiy yuksaklikda ifodalangan.

Bugungi kunda Navoiy merosining o‘rganilishi faqat milliy adabiyotshunoslik doirasida emas, balki global madaniy muloqot va sivilizatsiyalararo tafakkur kontekstida ham dolzarbdir. Shu bois “Saddi Iskandariy” dostoni zamonaviy ilmiy izlanishlarda Sharq va G‘arb adabiy tafakkurini bog‘lovchi estetik-falsafiy ko‘prik sifatida baholanmoqda.

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СИМВОЛИЧЕСКОЕ И РЕЛИГИОЗНОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБРАЗА ПАСТУХА

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется образ пастуха как одного из древнейших и универсальных символов в истории, отражающего связь человека с природой, идеи мудрости, простоты и заботы. Рассматриваются его символические и религиозные корни. Эволюция образа пастуха в современной жизни, а также значение в контексте различных эпох и культур.

Ключевые слова: пастух, пастырь, Израиль, Амос, сикхизм, символизм, природа, мифология, ассоциация, паства.

Введение

Пастушество – одно из древнейших областей деятельности, зародившееся около 5000 лет назад в Анатолии т.е. в Малой Азии. Овец разводили ради молока, мяса и особенно шерсти. В течение следующих тысячелетий овцеводство и пастушество распространились по всей Евразии. Анри Флейш предположил, что пастушеская неолитическая культура в Ливане может относиться к эпипалеолиту и что она могла использоваться одной из первых культур кочевых пастухов в долине Бекаа.

Несколько овец были пристроены на семейную ферму вместе с другими животными, такими как куры и свиньи. Чтобы содержать большое стадо, овцы должны иметь возможность переходить с пастбища на пастбище. Это потребовало развития профессии, отдельной от фермерской. Обязанностью пастухов было содержать свое стадо в целостности, защищать его от хищников и направлять на рынки вовремя для стрижки. В древние времена пастухи также обычно доили своих овец и делали из этого молока сыр; немногие пастухи до сих пор делают это.

Во многих обществах пастухи были важной частью экономики. В отличие от земледельцев, пастухи часто работали за плату, присматривая за чужими овцами. Пастухи также жили отдельно от общества, в основном кочуя. В основном это была работа для одиноких мужчин без детей, и поэтому новых пастухов приходилось нанимать со стороны. Пастухами чаще всего становились младшие сыновья земледельцев, которые не наследовали землю. В других обществах в каждой семье был член семьи, который пас стадо, часто это был ребёнок, юноша или старик, который не мог выполнять тяжёлую работу. Эти пастухи были полностью интегрированы в общество.

Пастухи обычно работали группами, присматривая за одним большим стадом или за своими собственными стадами и объединяя свои обязанности. Они жили в небольших хижинах, часто вместе со своими овцами, и покупали еду в местных общинах. Реже пастухи жили в крытых фургонах, которые передвигались вместе со стадами.

Овцеводство развивалось только в определённых регионах. В низинах и речных долинах было гораздо эффективнее выращивать зерновые культуры, чем пасти овец, поэтому овцеводство было сосредоточено в труднопроходимых и гористых районах. Таким образом, в доисторические времена овцеводство было сосредоточено в таких регионах, как Ближний Восток, Греция, Пиренеи, Карпаты, Шотландия и Северная Англия. Услуга пастуха может быть дорогостоящим. Кроме того, уничтожение хищников, охотящихся на овец, в некоторых регионах мира снизило потребность в пастухах.

В переносном смысле термин пастух (пастырь) используется для обозначения Бога, особенно в иудео-христианской традиции (например, Псалом 22, Иезекииль 34), а в христианстве – для обозначения Иисуса, который называл себя Добрым Пастухом. Древние израильтяне были пастушеским народом, и среди них было много пастухов. Также стоит отметить, что многие библейские персонажи были пастухами, в том числе патриархи Авраам и Иаков, двенадцать колен Израилевых, пророк Моисей, царь Давид и ветхозаветный пророк Амос, который был пастухом в гористой местности вокруг Текоа. В Новом Завете ангелы возвестили пастухам о рождении Иисуса.

Та же метафора применяется и к священникам: у римско-католических, лютеранских и англиканских епископов в качестве отличительного знака есть посох пастуха (см. также Ликида). В обоих случаях подразумевается, что верующие – это «стадо», за которым нужно присматривать. Отчасти это связано с наставлением Иисуса Петру: «Паси овец Моих», которое является источником пастырского образа в Ликиде.

Термин «пастор», изначально обозначавший «пастуха» на латыни, теперь используется исключительно для обозначения духовенства большинства христианских конфессий.

«Добрый пастырь» - одна из основных тем Священного Писания. Эта иллюстрация охватывает множество идей, в том числе заботу Бога о Своем народе. Склонность людей подвергать себя опасности и их неспособность направлять себя и заботиться о себе без непосредственной помощи и руководства Бога также подкрепляется метафорой овец, нуждающихся в пастыре.

Согласно Мухаммеду, пророку ислама, каждый посланник Бога в какой-то момент своей жизни был пастухом, как и он сам в молодости. Передал Джабир ибн Абдулла: «Мы были с Посланником Аллаха, когда он собирал плоды с деревьев арак, и Посланник Аллаха (мир ему и благословение Аллаха) сказал: «Соберите чёрные плоды, они самые лучшие». Сподвижники спросили: «Ты был пастухом?» Он ответил: «Не было пророка, который не был бы пастухом». (Сахих Бухари, глава «Пророки», том 4, книга 55, хадис 618) Сюда входят Иисус, Моисей, Авраам и все остальные пророки, согласно исламу.

В сикхизме также часто упоминаются пастушьи сказки. Есть много соответствующих цитат, например: «Мы – скот, Всевышний – наш пастырь».

Образ пастуха является одним из важнейших библейских мессианских образов. И в Ветхом, и в Новом Завете мы достаточно часто встречаемся с упоминанием пастуха. И это неудивительно, поскольку главным занятием предков древнего еврейского народа было скотоводство. Еще в первых главах первой библейской книги мы читаем о том, что именно жертва пастуха Авеля была наиболее приятна Богу.

И в дальнейшем, занятие пастушеством считалось в высшей степени почетным. Это видно и на примере Давида, который из пастухов был призван в цари: «Я взял тебя от стада овец, чтобы ты был вождем народа Моего, Израиля (2 Цар. 7:8). И, вероятно, не случайно Амос, первый письменный библейский пророк был призван к пророческому служению от пастушества: «Я не пророк и не сын пророка; я был пастух и собирал сикоморы» (Ам. 7:14) (см также Ам. 1:1). В книге пророка Исаии Бог называет своим пастырем персидского царя Кира (Ис. 44:28). В своих эсхатологических пророчествах пророк Иеремия говорит о будущих пастырях, которые будут пасти со знанием и благоразумием (Иер. 3:15).

О пастыре говорится и на страницах книги пророка Михея, современника пророков Исаии и Амоса. В пророчестве Михея о рождении Мессии в Вифлееме сообщается о том, что сам Мессия станет пастырем для сынов Израилевых, «и будет пасти в силе Господней, в величии имени Господа Бога Своего» (Мих. 5:4). К этому же пророчеству примыкает отрывок, в котором упоминается о семи пастырях, которые будут противостоять нашествию Ассира: «Когда Ассур придет в нашу землю и вступит в наши чертоги, мы выставим против него семь пастырей и восемь князей. И будут они пасти землю Ассира мечем и землю Немврода в самих воротах ее, и Он-то избавит от Ассира, когда тот придет в землю нашу и когда вступит в пределы наши» (Мих. 5:6). Очевидно, что под пастырями народа в данном месте подразумеваются князья народа. В 4 главе, описывая эсхатологические времена, пророк Михей представляет Бога как того, кто заботливо соберет хромых, разогнанных, рассеянных, то есть соберет Свой сокрушенный и отринутый прежде народ под Своей державой на Сионе (Мих. 4:6-7). В этих словах пророка Михея толкователи усматривают указание на создание Церкви Христовой, христианского народа, любящим пастырем которого является Господь Иисус Христос. В рассматриваемом отрывке Бог не называется напрямую пастырем, но

описание его деятельности напрямую связано с пастырской деятельностью, как она представлена в других библейских текстах.

В 7 главе этого же пророка мы встречаемся со сравнением народа Божия с овцами, а Бога – с пастырем. Пророк говорит о народе Бога как заблудшей пастве. Бог наказал свой народ, но он же и исцелит его (Мих. 7:11-20).

В пророческих текстах часто встречается противопоставление добрых пастырей, в том числе Самого Бога как пастыря («Я буду пасти овец Моих и Я буду покоить их, говорит Господь Бог» (Иез. 34:15)), и плохих, злых пастырей («Горе пастырям Израилевым, которые пасли себя самих! не стадо ли должны пасти пастыри?» (Иез. 34:2), (см. также Ис. 56:11)). Если первые заботятся о своих стадах, о своей пастве, то есть о народе, то вторые – только о самих себе.

Особое место образ пастыря занимает у пророка Иезекииля, созерцателя дивных видений, который был отведен в плен Вавилонский и пророчествовал в период с 592 по 563 год до Р. Х. [2, с. 462]. Пророк Иезекииль видел отверстыми горные врата и славу Божию. Он пророчествовал о Добром Пастыре – Сыне Человеческом (Иез. 34:30-31), о воскресении, первенцем которого стал Иисус Христос (Иез. 37:6-27). В книге Иезекииля имеется большое пророчество, посвященное пастырям народа Божия. Пророк критикует плохих пастырей, под которыми следует понимать руководителей народа, правителей и священников, которые заботились не о своей пастве, а только о себе самих: «Горе пастырям Израилевым, которые пасли себя самих! не стадо ли должны пасти пастыри? Вы ели тук и волною одевались, откормленных овец заколали, а стада не пасли. Слабых не укрепляли, и больной овцы не врачевали, и пораненной не перевязывали, и угнанной не возвращали, и потерянной не искали, а правили ими с насилием и жестокостью» (Иез. 34:2-4). В результате такой деятельности паства рассеялась: «И рассеялись они без пастыря и, рассеявшись, сделались пищею всякому зверю полевому. Блуждают овцы Мои по всем горам и по всякому высокому холму, и по всему лицу земли рассеялись овцы Мои, и никто не разведывает о них, и никто не ищет их» (Иез. 34:5-6). Бог отнимет паству у злых, недостойных пастырей и сам станет пасти ее: «Ибо так говорит Господь Бог: вот, Я Сам отыщу овец Моих и осмотрю их. Как пастух поверяет стадо своё в тот день, когда находится среди стада своего рассеянного, так Я пересмотрю овец Моих и высвобожу их из всех мест, в которые они были рассеяны в день облачный и мрачный. И выведу их из народов, и соберу их из стран, и приведу их в землю их, и буду пасти их на горах Израилевых, при потоках и на всех обитаемых местах земли сей. Буду пасти их на хорошей пажити, и загон их будет на высоких горах Израилевых; там они будут отдыхать в хорошем загоне и будут пастись на тучной пажити, на горах Израилевых» (Иез. 34:11-14). Бог будет настоящим пастырем, добрым, заботливым, справедливым пастухом: «Я буду пасти овец Моих и Я буду покоить их, говорит Господь Бог. Потерявшуюся отыщу и угнанную возвращу, и пораненную перевяжу, и больную укреплю, а разжиревшую и буйную истреблю; буду пасти их по правде» (Иез. 34:15-16).

Вместе с тем, пророк Иезекииль говорит о том, что Бог поставит над паствой своего нового пастыря, Давида (Мессию): «И поставлю над ними одного пастыря, который будет пасти их, раба Моего Давида; он будет пасти их и он будет у них пастырем. И Я, Господь, буду их Богом, и раб Мой Давид будет князем среди них. Я, Господь, сказал это. И заключу с ними завет мира и удалю с земли лютых зверей, так что безопасно будут жить в степи и спать в лесах» (Иез. 34:23-25). Из текста пророческой книги Иезекииля следует то, что Бог заботится о Своем народе, собирает

заблудших, помогает больным и дает Своему народу то, в чем тот нуждается – помощь и утешение, обетование.

Образ пастуха имеет большое значение в Ветхом Завете, поскольку и Бог, и Мессия представлены в нем как пастыри. В своих книгах ветхозаветные пророки осуждали злых пастырей, обещали дать новых пастырей, описывали качества этих пастырей, сравнивали народ с заблудшей паствой, которая будет собрана и исцелена Самим Богом, говорили о Боге и Давиде как подлинном пастыре народа.

Христианская Церковь под заблудшими овцами всегда понимала падший человеческий род, расширяя узкие границы еврейского народа. В Добром Пастыре Церковь всегда видела Иисуса Христа, воплотившееся Слово Божие, понесшее на Себе человечество – все естество человеческое.

В Новом Завете сам Иисус Христос широко использовал образ пастыря, представляя пастырем Самого Себя. При этом он не мог не иметь в виду и рассмотренные нами пророческие тексты. Поэтому и христиане зачастую видят во Христе доброго пастыря. Преподобный Симеон Новый Богослов с пламенной молитвой обращался к Доброму Пастырю, Человеколюбивому Богу, ко Христу: «Да, сочувствующий пастырь, благой и кроткий, желающий всем в Тебя верующим спастись, помилуй, услышь мою молитву...». Образ Христа как доброго пастыря используется и в христианской литургической традиции. Во время богослужения архиерей символизирует собой Христа как Доброго Пастыря. Об этом напоминает и малый архиерейский омофор, изображающий заблудшую овцу, под которой можно понимать и каждого заблудшего человека, и греховную человеческую природу в целом.

Персонаж пастуха в художественной литературе выступает неоднозначным символом, который отражает культурные, социальные и философские изменения разных эпох. Его изучение позволяет не только понять ключевые аспекты литературного наследия, но и глубже осмыслить вечные вопросы человеческого бытия: поиск гармонии, заботу о ближнем и стремление к мудрости. Изучение образа пастуха способствует воспитанию духа патриотизма у молодого поколения.

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HAMID OLIMJON DOSTONLARIDA SO‘ZLARNING SHAKL VA MA’NO MUNOSABATIGA KO‘RA TURLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Hamid Olimjon dostonlarida qo‘llangan so‘zlarning shakl va ma’no munosabatiga ko‘ra turlari tahlil qilinadi. Omonim, antonim, sinonim paronimlar orqali tilimizning nihoyatda boyligi va shu bilan bir qatorda borliqni va undagi narsa-predmetlarni ta’riflash va o‘z lisoniy manzarasida aks ettirish xususiyatlari namoyon bo‘ladi. Ularda ijodkorning voqelikni qay darajada idrok qilishi, voqelikka munosabati, tafakkuri, til birliklarini qo‘llash mahorati kabilar o‘z ifodasini topadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: antonim, sinonim, paronim, omonim, tazod, tuyuq, tajnis

O‘zbek adabiyotining yorqin, zabardast va iste’dodli shoirlaridan biri, dramaturg, olim va jamoat arbobi Hamid Olimjon hammamizga ma’lum va mashhur baxt va shodlik kuychisi sifatida tanilgan. Bugungi kunda nafaqat Hamid Olimjon, balki butun ijodkorlar ijodini chuqur o‘rganish, ular qo‘llagan har bir so‘zning bosh lug‘aviy va ko‘chma, ya’ni matniy ma’nolarini aniqlash, grammatik, leksik arxaiklashishi, davrlar o‘tishi bilan ma’noning kengayishi va torayishi, yangi ma’no kasb etishi, o‘ziga xos ijodkor ichki tuyg‘ularini tushunish kabi til bilimi bilan bog‘liq masalalarni ilmiy asoslash muhim tadqiqotlardan biridir. O‘zbek she’riyatida jo‘shqin lirizmga asoslangan she’riyat maktabini yaratgan shoir, dramaturg, olim Hamid Olimjonning badiiyatga yo‘g‘rilgan, hayotni va undagi go‘zallikni tarannum etgan betakror ijodi kishini hayratga soladi [1,15-bet]. Buyuk shoirning she’rlarida hayotning turli jabhalariga taalluqli bo‘lgan so‘z va atamalar ijodkor uslubiga xos o‘z badiiy ifodasini topgan. Bu esa, albatta, so‘z san’atkorining dunyoqarashi bilan bog‘liq kuzatuvchanlik, turli sohalarga bo‘lgan qiziquvchanlik, mulohazakorligidan darak beradi [5,21-bet]. Shoir nazmiy shaklda ifodalangan asarlarida badiiy tasvir vositalaridan, shuningdek, badiiy san’atlardan ustamonlik bilan foydalangan. Hammamizga ma’lumki, tilimizdagi so‘zlarning shakl va ma’no munosabatiga kora turlari, ya’ni omonim, sinonim, paronim, antonimlardan foydalanish badiiy asarning qimmatini oshiradi. Badiyatda antonimlardan tazod san’ati, omonimlardan tajnis sanati vositasida tuyuq janrini hosil qilish mumkin [3,177-bet]. Tilimizdagi so‘zlarning shakl va ma’no munosabatiga ko‘ra turlaridan shoir Hamid Olimjon ham mahorat bilan foydalangan. Jumladan:

U goyo bir buyuk tog‘

Yuzida ming yillik dog‘

Chunki zindon tagiga

Tashlangan bizning Oygul. (“Oygul bilan Baxtiyor”) [2, 109-bet]

Ushbu parchada **tog‘** – **dog‘** so‘zlari misolida talaffuzi, eshitalishi va morfem tarkibi o‘xshash, leksik ma’nolari boshqa-boshqa yoki qisman yaqinlik asosida yuzaga kelgan paronimlik munosabatini korishimiz mumkin.

Eshit, qizim Parizod,

Chiqaribsan yomon ot.

Sening bagring tosh emish,

Kozlaring beyosh emish,

Aslo sevmas emishsan,

Erga chiqmam, demishsan

Shartim shuki, ot bilan,

Goyoki qanot bilan

*Shu chinorga chiqqanga,
Chiqib uni yiqqanga
So'zsiz xotin bolaman,
Go'zal otin bolaman. (Semurg') [2,159-bet]*

Keltirilgan ushbu she'riy parchada esa omonimiya hodisasini ko'rishimiz mumkin: **ot** – **“shaxs nomi”** ma'nosida bo'lsa, **ot** – **“hayvon turi”** ma'nosida kelgan. Omonimlar - umumiy ma'no unsurlariga ega bo'lmagan, tasavvuriy bog'lanmagan, lekin bir xil yozilib, bir xil aytiladigan so'zlar, ular orasida semantik aloqa bo'lmaydi. Ana shunday so'zlarning tilda mavjud bo'lishi va shunga bog'liq hodisalar omonimiya deyiladi [4, 139-bet].

Tilda zid ma'noli so'zlarning mavjudligi badiiy nutqning ifodaliligi, ekspressivligi, ta'sirchanligini ta'minlashda qulay vositalardan biridir. Sharq adabiyotida juda qadim zamonlardan buyon tildagi bu ifoda imkoniyatidan keng foydalanib kelingan. Shoir uchun juda zarur bo'lgan san'atlardan biri tazoddir. Bu san'at yana mutobaqa, tiboq, tatbiq, muttazod, ittizod va takofu deb ham ataladi.

*O'zi balo tog'ining
Va ofat bulog'ining
Boshida o'ltirarmish,
Kun-u tun-u yoz ham qish.*

*Bunyod salqin soyada,
Bunday zo'r himoyada,
Yetti **tunni** uxladi,
Yetti **kunni** uxladi.*

*Qumlar ko'chib **erta-kech**,
Vatanidan ajraldi,
Sahro giyohsiz qoldi.*

*Qurtlar sarson bo'ldilar,
Uchgan qushlar o'ldilar (“Semurg'”) [2,120-bet].*

*Jambil edi bir **bo'ston**,
Qilding uni **go'riston**.*

*Senday qonxo'r zolimdan
Qolmasin deb biror zot,*

Bosh ko'tardik, zulmdan (“Oygul bilan Baxtiyor”) [2,107-bet].

Bu she'riy parchada esa antonimlar, ya'ni **kun-u tun, erta-kech, bo'ston-go'riston** kabi so'zlarni olishimiz mumkin. Antonimlar zid manoli til birliklari, ya'ni ma'nosi bir-biriga zid bo'lgan so'zlar antonim deyiladi. Antonimik juft hosil bo'lishi uchun ikkita mustaqil tushuncha ma'no jihatdan o'zaro qarama-qarshi bo'lishi kerak.

Ma'nodosh so'zlar tilning lug'aviy jihatdan boylik darajasini ko'rsatib beruvchi o'ziga xos vositadir. Tilda ma'nodosh so'zlarning ko'p bo'lishi tilning estetik vazifasini yana-da to'liq bajara olishini osonlashtiradi. Bu juda qadim zamonlardan beri anglangan, idrok etilgan va o'rganilgan hodisadir. O'zbek tili ma'nodosh so'zlarga juda boy. Yozuvchilar tilimizdagi ma'nodosh so'zlar ichidan tasvir maqsadiga eng munosibini topib ular orqali qahramonlar ruhiyati hamda tasvir obyektining eng kichik qirralarigacha ifodalashga harakat qiladilar [6,127-bet]. Badiiy matndagi ma'nodosh so'zlar tahlilida, asosan, ikki jihatga e'tiborni qaratish zarur. Ulardan biri muallifning ikki yoki undan ortiq ma'nodosh so'zdan ifodalanayotgan mazmun uchun eng maqbul birini tanlashi bo'lsa, ikkinchisi ayni bir matn tarkibida ikki yoki undan ortiq ma'nodosh birliklarni badiiy tasvir maqsadiga uyg'un holda qo'llashi masalasidir.

Xonni o'ldirmoq uchun,

Ko‘tarib elning kuchin

Kezardilar isyonda,

Ming alam, ming fig‘onda (“Oygul bilan Baxtiyor”) [2,107-bet].

Keltirilgan she‘riy parchada sinonimlar, ya‘ni alam, fig‘on kabi so‘zlarni olishimiz mumkin. Sinonimlar - bir umumiy ma‘noga ega bo‘lish hodisasi sinonimiya deyiladi. Bu hodisa qanday til birliklariga xosligiga qarab, lug‘aviy sinonimiya, frazeologik sinonimiya, sintaktik sinonimiya kabilarga bo‘linadi. Biz ulardan mosini, to‘g‘ri keladiganini tanlay bilishimiz zarur. Paronimlarda ham xuddi shunday. Ulardan nutqimizda foydalanish jarayonida katta e‘tibor talab etiladi. Birgina tovush o‘zgarishi butun bir so‘z ma‘nosini o‘zgartirib yuboradi. Bu esa matn mazmuniga ta‘sir etmay qolmaydi. Antonimlarda ham to‘g‘ri juftini tanlay bilish talab etiladi. Biz yuqorida ko‘rib o‘tgan Hamid Olimjonning ijodida bu talablarning barchasiga rioya qilinganligini, ularning o‘z o‘rnida ishlatilganligini va shu bilan bir qatorda keng foydalanganligini ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

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MILLIY MUMTOZ ADABIYOTIMIZ QOSID TIMSOLI QO‘LLANILISHINING ILDIZI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada milliy mumtoz adabiyotimiz xususan, she‘riyatida qosid timsoli qo‘llanilishining ildizi, adabiyotimiz xazinasidan o‘rin olgan she‘riy asarlar muayyan bir sana bilan chegaralangan bo‘lishiga qaramay, ancha uzoqlarga borib taqalishi haqidagi fikrlar muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Qosid, timsol, she‘riyat, mumtoz, lirik qahramon, she‘riy asarlar, xabarchi, uyg‘onish davri.

Bunga qo‘shimcha qilib aytishimiz mumkinki, ma‘shuqadan ayro tushib, hajr o‘tida yongan oshiq o‘z holatining qanday ekanligini yoriga etkazish uchun uchinchi bir shaxsga ehtiyoj sezadi. Mumtoz adabiyotimizda ana shu ehtiyoj tufayli, ya‘ni oshiqdan ma‘shuqaga xabar etkazish uchun ular o‘rtasida turadigan xabarchi – qosid timsoli yaratilgan. Qosid – 1. Elchi, xabarchi. 2. Qasd qiluvchi, niyat etuvchi [1, 67-b].

“O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati”da quyidagi ta‘rifni o‘qiymiz:

Qosid – (arabcha, قاصد – jo‘nab ketayotgan; intiluvchi, qasd qiluvchi; xabarchi, elchi, chopar) esk.kt. 1. ayn. xabarchi. 2. Qasd qiluvchi, intiluvchi[2, 346-b].

Biz berilgan bu ta‘riflardan so‘zning birinchi ma‘nosiga diqqatni qaratamiz.

Demak, qosid tushunchasi bir kishidan ikkinchi kishiga xabar olib boradigan kishini anglatarkan, adabiyotimizda bu timsolning shakllanishi, tadrijiyati, asar g‘oyasini bayon qilishdagi hamda badiiyatidagi o‘rnini tahlil va talqin qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

XXI asrning birinchi o‘n yilligida navoiyshunoslar orasida D.Salohiy, N.Bekova, D.Yusupova, Z.Mamadaliyeva, M.Tojiboyeva, E.Nasrullayev, S.O‘tanova singari

olimlarning tadqiqotlari katta avlod navoiyshunoslar boshlagan xayrli ishning munosib davomi bo'ldi desak mublag'a bo'lmaydi.

Biroq yuqorida qayd etilgan tadqiqotchilarning ishlari orasida Navoiy ijodidagi muayyan bir timsol tadqiqiga maxsus bag'ishlangan monografik tadqiqotlar nihoyatda kamsonli, mavjudlari ham boshqa bir mavzuni ochib berishga xizmat qilishi maqsadida yo'l-yo'lakay zikr etib kelingan. Jumladan, N.Komilov, E.Shodiyev, D.Yusupova, L.Zohidov kabi olimlarimizning ilmiy izlanishlari Navoiy ijodidagi timsollarning ma'lum bir jihatlari tadqiqiga bag'ishlangan.

XV asr o'zbek she'riyatining yirik namoyandalaridan biri, Navoiy ta'biri bilan aytganda, "turkigo'y mashohirdin..." sanalgan zullisonayn shoir Gadoiy sanaladi. Gadoiy ijodida ham qosidga murojaat uchraydi. Jumladan, Shoirning "Ohkim, devona ko'nglum mubtalo bo'ldi yana..." matla'li g'azalida shunday bayt bor:

Chini zulfingdin dam urmog'liq ne nisbat, ey abir,

Bu kinoyat bori sendin, bas, xato bo'ldi yana.

Baytdagi tushunilishi qiyin so'zlarning ma'nolarini aniqlashtirib olamiz: *abir, kinoyat.*

Abir – xushbo'y hid, anbar.

Kinoyat – kesatiq, piching, qochiriq.

Endi bayt tahlilini qaraymiz: xush iforli sochlaringdan so'zlamog bilan sening hamma qochiriqlaringning qanday o'xshashligi bor, ey anbar, endi bas, bari xato bo'ldi.

Ko'rinadiki, shoir qosid vazifasini baytda abir, ya'ni anbarga topshiryapti. An'anaviy she'riyatda yorning xushbo'y iforli sochidan xabar beruvchi timsol sifatida sabo keltirilsa, Gadoiy uning o'rnida xushbo'y ifor, ya'ni abir timsolidan foydalanadi. Bu bilan u badiiy tasvirlashga yangilik olib kira olgan, deyish mumkin.

Gadoiyning "Ey ko'ngul, dilbar xayoli chunki hamdamdur sanga" matla'li g'azaliga [3, 23-b] mansub quyidagi baytni tahlil qilamiz:

Qon yutarmen rashk elindin har kecha tongg'a degin

Kim, nechuk bodi sabo hamrozu hamdamdur sanga.

Tabdili: *har kecha tongga qadar rashk qo'ldan qon yutaman, bunga sabab tong shamolining senga sirdosh va hamdam ekanligidir.*

Baytda garchi bodi saboning biror bir narsadan xabar keltirayotganligi haqida so'z bormayotgan bo'lsa-da, u ma'shuqaga sirdosh va hamdam timsoli sifatida gavdalanyapti. Albatta, oshiq yo ma'shuqaga sirdosh bo'lgan shaxs yoki narsaning ulardan birining ahvoli haqida ikkinchisiga xabar etkazishi hayotiy haqiqatdir. Chunonchi, xalq shoiri, O'zbekiston Qahramoni Abdulla Oripov aytganlaridek,

Muhabbat bobida u-ku bir mahram,

Uningsiz visol hamyo'qdir aslida.

Shoirning yor uchun bitgan she'rin hamh

Yod olgan o'shadir she'rxon shaklida[4, 419-b].

Atoyi qalamiga mansub quyidagi g'azalning matla'sida nasim timsoli endi xabarchi emas, balki yor zulfidan taralayotgan yoqimli shamol, ya'ni o'z ma'nosida qo'llangan bo'lsa, xabarchi vazifasini boshqa timsol – sabobajarmoqda:

Mujda berdi subhidam zulfing nasimidin sabo,

Jon muattar bo'ldi, ko'nglum topti yuz turluk safo[5, 23-b].

Baytdagi so'zlarning hammasi deyarli tushunarli, faqat *safo* so'zining ma'nosini aniqlashtirib olamiz.

Safo – 1. Poklik, tozalik, tiniqlik. 2. Go'zallik. 3. Tinchlik, sulh, osoyishtalik.

Safo – (arabcha, صفاء – tozalik, tiniqlik, soflilik; samimiylik; xotirjamlik) 1. Beg'ubor tozalik, musaffolik, soflilik. 2. Xursandchilik kayfiyati, nash'u namo; huzur, gasht.

Baytdagi *nasim* soʻzi ham oʻz maʼnosi – *shamol* maʼnosida emas, balki *soch* soʻziga bogʻlanib, koʻchma maʼnoda – *muloyim ifor* maʼnosida kelyapti. Sabo soʻzi ertalab esadigan mayin va yoqimli shabadani anglatadi va odatda, u biror yaxshilik xabari bilan bogʻliq boʻladi

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, bayt shunday sharhlansa boʻladi: erta tongda mayin esgan shabada sochlarningningmuloyim iforidan xabar bergach, jonim xush boʻylarga toʻlib, koʻnglim yuz turli huzur topdi.

Xulosa qilib aytganimizda, Milliy sheʼriyatimizda Ilk Uygʻonish davri adabiyotida qosid timsoli alohida ahamiyat kasb eta bordi. Yusuf Xos Hojib, Xorazmiy ijodida bu timsolga murojaat nisbatan kamroq uchrasa-da, Atoyi va Gadoiy sheʼriyatidan boshlab qosid timsoli sheʼriyatda mustahkam oʻrin egallagan, yaʼni ularning sheʼriyatida qosid timsoliga murojaat bir muncha koʻp uchraydi. Qosid vazifasini sabo, tong eli, nasim, shamol, roviy va, hatto, abir (anbar) timsollari bajargan.

Demak, qosid timsoli sheʼriyatimizning Navoiy davrigacha boʻlgan taraqqiyot bosqichlarida toʻla shakllanib, mumtoz adabiyotimizdagi anʼanaviy timsollar safidan joy olgan va sheʼriyatimizning ajralmas qismiga aylanib ulgurgan.

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SOBIR OʻNAR NASRIY MEROSINING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy adabiyotshunoslikning yorqin vakillaridan biri boʻlgan Sobir Oʻnar nasriy merosining shakllanish bosqichlari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tadqiq qilingan. Adibning asarlaridagi badiiy soʻz sanʼatining adabiy taʼlimiga qoʻshgan hissalari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar. Til, soʻz sanʼati, adabiyot, ruhiy holat, axloqiy tanlov, obraz, ruhiyat, shakl, dramatism.

Soʻz sanʼatining mohiyati shundaki, u insonni oʻylantiradi, quvontiradi, qaygʻuga soladi, oʻtmish va kelajak haqida mushohada yuritishga undaydi. Adabiyot asarlarida faqat syujet yoki voqelik emas, balki ularni qanday tasvirlash, qanday soʻzlar orqali ifodalash ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shu jihatdan adabiyot boshqa fan va sanʼat turlaridan ajralib turadi. Masalan, tarix voqeani faktlar orqali, falsafa esa fikrlar orqali ifodalasa, adabiyot buni obrazlar, ramzlar va badiiy tasvirlar orqali beradi. Demak, adabiyotda goʻzallikni yaratish – bu soʻzlar orqali sanʼat asarini vujudga keltirishdir. Adabiy tanqidchi Qozoqboy Yoʻldoshevning quyidagi gaplari ham fikrimiz tasdigʻidir: “Adabiyot – abadiyatga daʼvogar. Adib betizgin vaqtini tizginlashga urinadigan zot. U tarixchidan farq qilaroq, zamon haqida axborot, maʼlumot bermaydi. Bilaks, vaqtini, odam umrining biror qismini hissiyot-u sezimlari bilan tasvirga muhrlab, toʻxtatib qoʻyadi”. [1] Adabiyotning azaliy namunalaridan

tortib zamonaviy badiiy asarlargacha bo‘lgan asarlarda so‘zning badiiy kuchi va san’atkorona ishlatilishi ustuvor ahamiyat kasb etadi. Jumladan, Alisher Navoiy, Atoiy, Abdulla Qodiriy, Oybek, Mirtemir kabi ijodkorlar o‘z asarlarida so‘zning san’atga aylanishiga erishgan ijodkorlardir. Ularning asarlarida har bir jumla nafaqat ma’no, balki musiqiylik, ohangdorlik, badiiy zavq manbai sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Sobir O‘nar (to‘liq ismi-sharifi: O‘narov Sobir Hamzayevich) - o‘zbek adabiyotining XX–XXI asrlar oralig‘idagi fidoyi va samimiy so‘z san’atkori, yozuvchi, muharrir, tarjimon va publitsist sifatida o‘zining betakror ijodi bilan milliy adabiyotimizni boyitgan chinakam ijodkor edi. U 1964-yil 25-fevralda Samarqand viloyatining Qo‘shrabot tumani, Quvkalla qishlog‘ida dunyoga keldi. Tabiat bag‘rida ulg‘aygan bu bola kelajakda inson va jamiyat, orzu va iztirob, haqiqat va qalb ohanglarini yurakdan his etib, yozishga, ifodalashga, qalamlashga oshno bo‘ldi. Maktabni tamomlab, Toshkent davlat universitetining (hozirgi O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti) jurnalistika fakultetida tahsil oldi. 1986-yilda oliygohni tugatgan yosh yigit darrov matbuot olamiga sho‘ng‘idi. Bu sho‘ng‘ish oddiy kasbiy faoliyat emas, balki hayotini adabiyotga, so‘zga, jamiyatga bag‘ishlashning ilk qadami edi [1].

Sobir O‘nar ijodining ilk bosqichi 1980-yillarning oxiri va 1990-yillar boshlarida boshlangan bo‘lib, bu davr uning ijodiy izlanish, shakllanish va adabiy sahnaga kirib kelish jarayoni bo‘lgan. Yozuvchining dastlabki hikoya va esselari matbuot sahifalarida paydo bo‘la boshladi. Bu asarlar ko‘proq insoniylik, halollik, e‘tiqod, muhabbat kabi umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni yoritishga yo‘naltirilgan bo‘lib, yozuvchi bu mavzularni sodda, lekin obrazli va hayotiy tarzda bayon qilardi. Uning ilk hikoyalaridan boshlab o‘quvchi o‘ziga tanish ruhiy holatlar, axloqiy tanlovlar, turmushdagi oddiy, ammo muhim tafsilotlarni his qilgan. Bu davr ijodida hikoya janri yetakchi bo‘lib, unda real hayot manzaralari, kundalik tashvishlar orqali katta ijtimoiy va axloqiy fikrlar ilgari surilgan. Dastlabki asarlarining o‘zidayoq u adabiy tanqidning e‘tiboriga tushdi, sababi o‘ziga xos tilda, badiiy tahlil va falsafiy yondashuvda yozar, o‘quvchini oddiy gaplar ortidagi chuqur ma’nolarni anglashga majbur qilardi.

Ijodining keyingi bosqichi – 1990-yillarning ikkinchi yarmi va 2000-yillar davomida yozuvchi badiiy kamolotga erishadi. Bu bosqichda u insonning ichki olamiga chuqur kirib boradi, ruhiy-ma’naviy jarayonlarni falsafiy tahlillar bilan boyitadi. Bu asarlar faqat bir inson hayoti yoki hodisasi haqida emas, balki jamiyatdagi umumiy ruhiy muhit, ma’naviy qashshoqlik, qadriyatlar tanazzuli, “mohiyat” va “shakl” orasidagi nomuvofiqlik kabi murakkab masalalarni badiiy tilda ifoda etishga qaratilgan. Sobir O‘nar uchun nasr – bu jamiyatni o‘rganish vositasi, insonning ruhiy iqlimini tahlil qilish maydoni edi. Uning qahramonlari tashqi harakatdan ko‘ra ichki iztirob, o‘y-mulohazaga berilgan odamlar bo‘lib, ular orqali yozuvchi inson qalbidagi haqiqat izlanishini yoritadi. Shubilan birga, bu davrda uning yozuvchilik pozitsiyasi yanada aniqlandi – u ijtimoiy tanqidchi emas, ma’naviy ogohlikka da’vat etuvchi ijodkor sifatida shakllandi.

Sobir O‘nar o‘zining nasriy merosida voqeani emas, voqealikni, odamni emas, odamzodiylikni, gapni emas, ma’noni yozdi. Ana shu xususiyatlari uni zamonaviy o‘zbek adabiyotining teran, mulohazali, yurak bilan fikr qiladigan yozuvchilari qatoriga olib chiqdi.

Ijodining so‘nggi yillari – 2000-yillar oxiri va 2010–2020-yillarda esa Sobir O‘nar o‘zining yetuk badiiy-falsafiy asarlarini yaratadi. Bu davrda u hikoya, qissa bilan birga esse va publitsistik asarlarga ham murojaat qiladi. Uning asarlarida millat, tarix, zamon haqida chuqur falsafiy mushohadalar, ziyolilarning ijtimoiy mas’uliyati, vijdon va imon, hayot va o‘lim, sinov va najot kabi mavzular markazga chiqadi. “Ko‘zgudagi aks”, “Jasorat”, “Najot”, “Xat” kabi asarlarida yozuvchi ijtimoiy muammolarga murojaat qilardi ekan, ularni siyosiy nuqtai nazardan emas, balki axloqiy-ruhoniylar orqali yoritadi. Yozuvchining tili yanada tiyin-tiyiq, obrazlari chuqur ramziy va hayotiy bo‘ladi. U matn orqali emas, ruh orqali

gapiradi; voqelikni emas, voqelik ortidagi mohiyatni ochadi. Aynan shu xususiyatlar Sobir O'narning nasrini boshqalarnikidan ajratib turadi. Unga ko'ra, yozuvchi jamiyatga faqat oynani tutmasligi, balki haqiqatni anglashga yordam beradigan ko'zgu yasashi kerak.

U 1986-yildan boshlab uzoq yillar davomida „Yoshlik“ jurnalida ishlab, o'zining jurnalistlik va muharrirlik mahoratini namoyon qildi. Avval muharrir, so'ng bo'lim boshlig'i, bosh muharrir o'rinbosari, keyinchalik esa jurnalning bosh muharriri lavozimlarida faoliyat yuritdi. Yillar davomida „Yoshlik“ sahifalarida bosilgan ko'plab adabiy, ma'naviy, dolzarb maqola va asarlar ortida Sobir O'narning ziyrak nigohi, mehrlil qalbi, halol muharrirlik mas'uliyati turardi. U nafaqat o'z ijodi bilan, balki yuzlab yosh qalamkashlar, iste'dodlar yo'lini yoritgan, ularga ishonch bilan yo'l ochgan ustoz sifatida ham esda qolgan.

2015-yildan hayotining oxirigacha „Kuch adolatda“ gazetasida mas'ul kotib, „G'afur G'ulom“ va „Yoshlar“ nashriyotlarida muharrir, Yozuvchilar uyushmasining „Nasr“ bo'limida faoliyat yuritdi. Bu lavozimlar oddiy ish joyi emasdi - ular adabiyotning buguni va ertangi kunini belgilovchi ijodiy muhitning yuragi edi. Sobir O'nar bu muhitda nafaqat ishtirokchi, balki yo'naltiruvchi, ilhom beruvchi, yangi avlod qalamkashlarini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi ustoz sifatida tanildi. Sobir O'nar ijodga juda erta, talabalik yillaridayoq kirib keldi. 1986-yilda „Yoshlik“ jurnalida ilk hikoyalari chop etildi va bu kichik qadam uning butun hayot yo'lini belgilab berdi. So'zga mehr, qalbga sezgirlik va hayotga samimiy nazar uning ijodining asosiy tamoyiliga aylandi.

1989-yilda e'lon qilingan dastlabki kitobi - „Orzuga to'la qishloq“ adabiy olamda iliq kutib olindi. Bu nom bejiz tanlanmagan edi: unda qishloq hayotining o'ziga xos ranglari, odamlarning orzu-umidlari, kelajakka intilishi, beg'ubor istaklari mujassam edi. Har bir hikoya hayotning o'zi kabi tabiiy, inson qalbi kabi murakkab va samimiy edi. Keyingi yillarda dunyo yuzini ko'rgan „Ovloq adirlar bag'rida“, „Chashma“, „Inqilob kechasi“, „Dunyo shundoq tururmi?“, „Bibisora“, „Farishta“, „Kunsuluvning sirli xatlari“ kabi qissa va hikoyalar ham ana shu ruhning davomchisi bo'ldi. U qahramonlarini ulug'lash yoki kamsitishdan yiroq edi - ular hayotda qanday bo'lsa, asarda ham shunday jonli, tabiiy, kamchiliklari va fazilatlarini bilan birga tasvirlanardi. Ayniqsa, „Dunyo shundoq tururmi?“ va „Bibisora“ qissalari adabiy jamoatchilikda katta e'tibor uyg'otdi. Bu asarlar haqida atoqli adiblar - Odil Yoqubov, Abdulla Oripov, Halima Xudoyberdiyeva, shuningdek, taniqli adabiyotshunos olimlar M.Qo'shjonov, B.Nazarov, T.Mirzayevlar iliq fikr bildirdi. Bu esa Sobir O'narning adabiyotdagi mavqeini mustahkamlash bilan birga, uning g'oyaviy-estetik salohiyatini ham tasdiqladi.

Sobir O'nar uchun yozish - shunchaki kasb emas, qalbning buyuk ehtiyoji edi. U so'z orqali insonning ichki olamiga kirar, dardini, quvonchini, orzularini, iztiroblarini tinglar va ularga badiiy shakl berar edi. Uning nasrida sun'iylik, bezakli so'zlar ortidagi bo'shlik yo'q - u hayotning o'zi kabi samimiy, odamlar kabi haqiqiy. Bugun Sobir O'narni eslaganda, ko'z oldimizda qalamini o'tkir, qalbini esa keng tutgan, adabiyotga fidoyi inson obrazi jonlanadi. U o'zbek nasrida sof insoniylik, pokiza tuyg'u va samimiy badiiyat timsoli bo'lib qoldi. Uning asarlari esa yangi avlodni ham hayotga, ezgulikka, so'zga muhabbat bilan qarashga chorlaydi.

Sobir O'nar - so'zga sadoqat bilan yashagan, inson ruhiyatini noziklik bilan tasvirlagan, samimiylilik va oriyat bayrog'ini baland tutgan adibdir. Uning asarlari bugun ham o'quvchini o'ziga tortadi, qalblarga yetib boradi, yuraklarni larzaga soladi. U ijodda insonparvarlik, haqiqat va mehr-muhabbatni ulug'lagan, so'z orqali yuksak badiiyat yaratgan ijodkor sifatida qalblarda yashaydi. Asarlari esa o'zbek adabiyoti xazinasida mangu qoladi.

Yuqorida aytib o'tganimizdek, yozuvchining adabiyot sahnasiga qo'ygan dastlabki qadamlarini belgilagan asarlar sifatida „Kunsuluvning sirli xatlari“ va „Qish kunlaridan biri“

hikoyalari alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu ikki hikoya 1986-yilning avgust oyida “Yoshlik” jurnalining 8-sonida e’lon qilinib, o’sha davr o’quvchilari orasida katta qiziqish uyg’otgan edi [2]. Asarlar mazmunida muallifning o’ziga xos kuzatuvchanligi, oddiy hayot manzaralarini chuqur ma’naviy qatlamlar bilan uyg’unlashtira olish mahorati, inson ruhiy olamiga kirib borishdagi nozikligi yaqqol seziladi. “Kunsuluvning sirli xatlari” hikoyasi orqali yozuvchi o’zbek qishlog’i hayotidagi samimiy tuyg’ular, insoniy orzu va armonlarni ifodalashga intilgan. Asardan olingan quyidagi parcha so’zimiz isbota bo’la oladi: “Bu voqeani u unutgani yo’q. Bir kun kelib o’sha qizni yana uchratganday bo’ldi. Biroq buning nomi bo’lakcha – Kunsuluv. Tag’in uni “amma” deb emas, “yanga” deb chaqiradi. Eng chatog’i – yangasi uning ismini aytib chaqira olmaydi. Nima emish “Hushtakchi” emish. Yangasi shunday deb chaqirsa o’zini u ulg’ayib qolgandek his qiladi va qo’llarini musht qilib, ikki barmog’ini og’ziga tiqadi-da, bulbulcha bo’lib bir sayraydiki asti qo’yavering”[2]. Ushbu voqea o’zbek qishloq hayotiga xos samimiylik, o’zaro yaqin munosabatlar va milliy qadriyatlarning o’zida mujassam bo’lgan bir lavha sifatida talqin etilishi mumkin. Qahramon bir vaqtlar uchratgan qizni oradan ancha vaqt o’tgach, yana ko’rganday bo’ladi. Ammo bu safar uning holati boshqacha – qiz endi boshqa nom bilan ataladi: Kunsuluv. Qolaversa, qahramon unga o’xshagan qizni ilgari “amma” deb chaqirgan bo’lsa, endi bu qizga “yanga” deb murojaat qiladi. Bu o’zgarish qishloq muhitida qarindoshlik va ijtimoiy munosabatlar tizimining qay darajada nozik va ko’p qatlamli ekanini ko’rsatadi.

Kunsuluv bor dardini xatlariga to’kar edi. Uning qo’llari qaltirardi. Har safar qog’oz ustiga qalam tekkanda, ichidagi butun bir olam silkinib ketardi. Harflar ketma-ket yasalardi, ammo so’zlar juda og’ir tushardi. Go’yo yuragidan uzib olib, qog’ozga qo’yayotgandek. Xatlarida u hech qachon “Men seni sevaman” degan oddiy jumlaning yozmagan. Ammo har bir satr, har bir jumla, hatto har bir tinish belgisi o’sha so’zning o’rnini bosardi. U shunday yozardiki, oq qog’ozdagi qora harflar erining qo’liga iliqlik berardi. “Qoshlari qop-qora ekan... nahot umr bo’yi izlaganim shu bo’lsa...” [2] - bu jumla qisqa bo’lishiga qaramay, unda inson ruhiyatidagi keskin burilish nuqtasi mujassam. Birinchi jumla tashqi belgini qayd etadi - qora qosh obrazning diqqatga sazovor jihati sifatida tilga olinadi. Ikkinchi jumla esa ichki kechinmani ochadi: uzoq izlangan va tasavvurda yaratilgan timsolning kutilmagan lahzada topilgandek tuyulishi. Ushbu ifoda shaxsning hissiy holatini ochiq-oydin ko’rsatadi - unda hayrat, ichki uyg’onish va quvonch uyg’unlashgan. Shu tariqa, oddiy ko’ringan tasvir ortida murakkab ruhiy jarayon va hayotiy izlanishlar manzarasi yotadi. Kunsuluv erini qattiq sevardi. Buni hech kimga aytmadi, hattoki unga ham. Ammo bu sevgi aytilmagan bo’lsa-da, yashirin bo’lsa-da, ko’zlarida, mayin tabassumida, unga suzgan choyida, kechasi uxlamay uning kiyimlarini tikayotganida sezilardi. U sevgisini so’z bilan emas, hayotning har bir mayda detali bilan ifodalay olardi. Ammo erining bilishini xohlasa-da, tiliga keltirib aytishning uddasidan chiqolmasdi. U yana bir maktubida: “Ming qatla shukr, Xolnazarim, menikisan, men ham senikiman! O’lsak o’ligimiz ortiq ulardan...”[2]. Bu jumla bir butun holda shunday ma’noni beradi: Ming marta shukr, ey Xolnazarim, sen meniki, men esa senikiman. Bizning bir-birimizga bo’lgan sadoqatimiz shunchalik kuchli va yuksakki, hatto o’lganda ham bizning nomimiz, ruhimiz va qadrimiz boshqalarnikidan ortiq bo’ladi. Bu yerda muhabbat, minnatdorlik va faxr uyg’unlashgan. Aytilayotgan so’zlar sevgining o’zaro ekanini va bu sevgi hayotdan ham, o’limdan ham ustun turishini ifodalaydi.

Yuqoridagi ikki hikoya ham o’ziga xos tarzda qishloq hayotining tabiiy, hayotiy manzaralarini yoritadi. Ularning markazida – oddiy insonlar, qishloq odamlari va ularning samimiy munosabatlari turadi. Muallif voqealarni murakkab syujetlar, zo’rma-zo’raki dramatismsiz, balki hayotning o’zi qanday bo’lsa, shunday holatda tasvirlaydi.

Qahramonlarning ichki kechinmalari, orzu-armonlari, dard va quvonchlari o'zlarining sodda, beg'ubor tili bilan ifodalanadi.

Muallif tilidagi samimiylik, tasvirlardagi tabiiylik o'quvchini voqealar ichiga olib kiradi, ularni qahramonlar bilan birga quvonishga va birga iztirob chekishga undaydi. Natijada, ikki hikoya ham qishloq kishilarining sof qalbini, milliy qadriyatlarni va qadrlı insoniy tuyg'ularni asrab qolish zarurligini eslatib, iliqlik va o'ziga xos ruhiy taskin baxsh etadi.

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НРАВСТВЕННЫЕ ЦЕННОСТИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ РАСПУТИНА И ИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается воздействие повести Валентина Распутина «Прощание с Матёрой» на нравственное воспитание молодого поколения. Автор анализирует художественные образы и этические проблемы, отражённые в произведении, подчёркивает значение духовных и моральных ценностей в формировании личности. Особое внимание уделено образу Дарьи как носительницы народной совести и хранительницы традиций, а также роли природы и родной земли в становлении нравственного сознания человека. Исследование показывает, что творчество Распутина способствует воспитанию любви к родному краю, уважения к памяти предков и осознанию ответственности человека перед природой и обществом.

Ключевые слова: этическое обучение, литературно-художественные стили, деловые публикации, популярные работа научного характера, иллюстрированные издания (альбомы), фантастическая литература, самосознание.

В.А. Сухомлинский писал: "Воспитание - это разносторонний процесс непрерывного духовного обогащения и обновления как воспитываемых, так и воспитывающих» [1, с. 270].

Этическое обучение - направленный на достижение цели процесс знакомства детей с ценностями человечества и конкретного общества.

Этические чувства - это внутренние переживания человека по поводу его поведения и отношения к окружающему миру. В этическом сознании личности эти чувства находятся в органическом соединении с этическими понятиями, составляя своеобразный сплав нравственного, разума и чувств.

Этическое обучение представляет собой один из элементов многообразного процесса становления личности, овладение индивидом моральными ценностями, формирование у него нравственных качеств, способности руководствоваться идеалом, следовать нормам и правилам морали, когда его убеждения и представления о должном выражаются в реальных поступках и поведении.

Термин "этика" согласно словарю русского языка по С.И. Ожегову определяется как внутренние, духовные стороны, по которым руководствуется человек; этические принципы; правила поведения, которые обусловлены этими сторонами. В данной дефиниции понятия "духовность" и "этика" во многом совпадают [2, с. 325].

Кроме того, в академической литературе термины "этика" и "мораль" часто раскрываются как синонимы. Этические принципы отражают общечеловеческие ценности, в то время как мораль зависит от особенностей жизни в различных слоях общества. По мере изменения социальной структуры общества изменяется и мораль, но этика остается постоянной категорией. Этическое обучение предполагает воздействие на личность с целью формирования ею этического сознания, развития этических чувств и овладения навыками и умениями этичного поведения.

Изумительно актуальной остается проблема прогресса духовной и нравственной культуры общества, и, соответственно, явственной становится необходимость школы обращаться к искусству как к ключевому средству выявления духовного потенциала личности, стимулирования его развития.

Тема привязанности к родной местности и проблема экологии являются центральными в повести "Прощание с Матерой" А. Распутина.

Авторская позиция, несомненно, вложена в уста Дарьи, главной героини повести. Она своего рода народный философ. Много повидала за свою долгую жизнь, накопила огромный жизненный опыт. Она имеет полное право называться носительницей народной правды, народной философии.

Повесть посвящена этическим проблемам, с которыми сталкиваются жители современной деревни. Сюжет извлечен из реального опыта писателя, что отчетливо видно при внимательном чтении.

Деревня матери писателя, попавшая под угрозу затопления при строительстве ГЭС, становится символом уходящего под воду исторического наследия. Затопление деревни и переезд приносят для некоторых трагедию, а для других оказываются лишь проходящим событием. Для старушек, которые прожили всю жизнь на этой земле и собрались умирать здесь, это становится настоящей трагедией. Они беспокоятся, как легко люди расстанутся со своими родными местами и как безразлично относятся к могилам, хранящим память о прошлом.

Между старшими и молодыми существуют огромные различия в восприятии мира. Для молодого парня, который прибыл, чтобы сжечь деревню, непонятно, почему старушке нужно убирать избу, которую все равно разрушат. Когда читаешь повесть, ощущаешь беспокойство и тревогу автора, который не ищет виноватых, не обеляет одних и не упрекает других, позволяя правде самой найти своё место в сердцах читателей.

Центральной темой повести является угасание духовных ценностей человечества. Люди забывают о совести, правде, святых местах и истории своего народа, которая передавалась из поколения в поколение. Спасением этого наследия занимается костяк деревни, сохраняя уникальную культуру, которой все гордились. Писателю удаётся передать народную жизнь с помощью простоты, точности и ясности языка.

Для углубленного понимания произведения Распутин использует лирическое отступление, которое показывает связь между людьми и природой.

Тема "Прощание с Матерой" остается актуальной и будет притягивать внимание на протяжении долгого времени. Писатель может продолжить эту тему в других повестях и рассказах, надеясь на отклик у читателей и их влияние на принятие решений. С течением времени меняются образ жизни, изменяются нравы, вызывая новые тревоги и беспокойства. Старая мудрость напоминает: плачьте не о погибшем, а об утраченной совести. Главный урок, который можно извлечь из этой повести, заключается в необходимости хранить духовное наследие и ценности народа.

Дарья обвиняет собственную сущность в обеднении души. Человек запутался в существовании, возомнив себя властелином природы, и делает с ней всё, что захочет. Человек не желает нести ответственность за судьбу природы и земли. Стать наблюдателем со стороны кажется проще и легче. По мнению Дарьи, люди утратили чувство совести и стыд перед другими. Им все равно, затопят Матери, или сожгут, лишь бы иметь место для жилья.

Дарья является олицетворением совести и морали народа. Она - хранительница этой морали. Дарья – воплощение совести и народной нравственности. Она её хранительница. Перед затоплением Дарья идёт на кладбище. Здесь покоится вся её родня: братья, сестра, прадеды, деды... Она винит себя за то, что не смогла отстоять их покой. Старуха хочет перенести родные могилки на новое место, хочет спасти их от кощунственного уничтожения. Память предков для неё - святое. Очень трогательной изображена сцена, где Дарья готовит свою избу в последний путь. Она вымыла каждую дощечку, каждое брёвнышко, побелила печку. Изба для неё не просто место проживания, это нечто большее, священное. Здесь прошла её жизнь, жизнь, её родителей, предков.

В чём автор видит нравственное величие Дарьи? Дарья как будто главная в деревне. К ней идут за советом, с ней считаются. Она всем помогает. Когда начали уничтожать кресты на кладбище, Богодул первым делом примчался к Дарье, зная, что она сможет дать отпор.

Как Дарья относится к Матёре? Что она для неё значит? Матёра для Дарьи – это не только деревня, где она родилась и прожила жизнь. Это мать- земля, это прочная, вечная крепость крестьянского уклада жизни. Для неё трагедия в том, что происходит гибель тысячелетнего человеческого уклада, выкорчёвывание жизни многих и многих поколений, стирание с лица земли целого природного мира, который был родным домом для человека. Дарья сама стала похожа на Матёру. Крепко держится за эту землю, с которой у неё общая судьба и одна правда. До конца своих дней женщина верна Матёре.

Дарья и Матёра – воплощение образа женщины – матери. Не случайно и Земля, и Природа, и деревня – всё женского рода. Их назначение – рожать, давать жизнь другому и вырастить, уберечь от бед, сохранить. Дарья понимает, что с развитием технического прогресса физические возможности самого человека нисколько не увеличились. «Какой был, такой и есть. Был о двух руках-ногах, боле не приросло», - с грустью произносит Дарья. Сама она уверена, что человек силён прежде всего своими корнями, традициями, памятью.

В чём Дарья видит причину нравственной катастрофы?

Причина – в разрушении связи с природой, с корнями. Дарья беспокоится об утрате нравственных ценностей, памяти: нельзя разрушить связь с природой и остаться нравственным. Финал повести трагический и в то же время открытый. Это оставляет надежду, что должно произойти нравственное пробуждение народа. Жива в людях ответственность за будущее природы и земли. «Жизнь на то она и жизнь, чтобы продолжаться, она всё перенесёт и примется везде, хоть и на голом камне и в зыбкой трясине...», - утверждает В.Распутин.

Что для этого необходимо?

Нельзя дать оскудеть душе, нельзя, чтобы очерствело сердце, надо жить в гармонии с природой, беречь память, ибо «правда в памяти. У кого нет памяти, у того нет жизни».

Люди, к сожалению не изменились ничуть. Поэтому литература конца XX века продолжала говорить о безнравственности и бездуховности. Проблемы оставались прежние, к ним добавлялись всё новые и новые.

Тема любви к родному краю и проблема экологии посвящена повесть Распутина «Прощание с Матёрой».

Таким образом в своем произведении "Прощание с Матерой", А. Распутин затрагивает широкий спектр проблем, включая экологические вопросы, исчезновение деревень, моральные дилеммы, ответственность человека за будущее страны, связь поколений, столкновение традиционного и современного, а также тему памяти.

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ДРАМАТУРГИЯ А. В. ВАМПИЛОВА В АСПЕКТЕ ТРАДИЦИИ И НОВАТОРСТВА

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Аннотация: в статье рассматривается творчество драматурга с точки зрения преимущества литературной традиции и новаторства. Автор выявил уникальность театра Вампилова и выявил основные специфические черты.

Ключевые слова: литературная традиция, теория бесконфликтности, театроведческий аспект, театр Вампилова, психологическая драма.

Особенностью 50-60-х годов XX века в истории русской драматургии являлась губительная для сценического искусства теория бесконфликтности, в соответствии с которой советское общество показывалось как идеальное, образцовое, практически без изъянов. В пьесах было изображено противостояние «хорошего с лучшим». Драматургам пришлось вести борьбу с этим явлением, в связи с чем центральное место заняла бытовая драма, сосредоточившая свое внимание на обычном человеке, его достоинствах и недостатках.

Вопросами разработки новых тем и конфликтов занимались такие писатели как А. Арбузов «Годы странствий» (1954), В.Розов «В добрый час!» (1955), Н. Погодин «Сонет Петрарки» (1956) и др. Их пьесы были посвящены преимущественно одной теме - теме становления молодых характеров.

Определенные сдвиги наметились прежде всего в самом подходе писателей к изображению жизненных явлений. Теперь на первый план выходят герои, которые идут к пониманию жизненных ценностей сложными путями. Это способствует тщательной

психологической разработке характеров. Все внимание сосредотачивается на внутреннем мире персонажей. Данный прием обусловил развитие драматических сюжетов, характеризующихся тяготением к усложненным психологическим конфликтам. Благодаря этому появляется гораздо больше пьес семейно-психологического или семейно-бытового плана, обращенных как правило к сфере личной жизни людей. Обращаясь к «личной теме», драматурги стремятся насытить свои произведения социально содержательными аспектами, наполнить их гражданским пафосом. Характерно также увеличение и расширение жанрового диапазона драматургии. Появляются сатирические комедии, драма (психологическая и героическая), трагедия (на историческом и современном материале). Арбузов предпринимает попытку создать трагикомедию («Двенадцатый час» (1959, перераб. 1980), мелодраму «Потерянный сын» (1960)).

Новые тенденции отчетливо проявляются в творчестве А. Вампилова. Его произведения занимают особое место в истории русской литературы.

С самых первых шагов в литературе в произведениях Вампилова видна была русская литературная традиция. Те проблемы и вопросы, которые он освещал (как жить, что такое счастье и почему оно у всех разное, как построить в себе «внутреннего человека» (выражение Гоголя)), звучали тревожно, а подчас и мрачно. «Что такое, собственно, счастье? Для одних - душевное равновесие, для других - материальное благополучие. Для третьих то и другое неотделимо. Для молодого человека с фантазией и эмоциями - это жить в шумном городе, где есть такой дворик и дом - вечером нажал кнопку - выбегает любимая девушка» [Вампилов, Из записных книжек]. Драматург как бы призывал своих читателей-зрителей самостоятельно ответить на все волнующие его ответы.

Драматургия Вампилова сочетает в себе истоки русской классики (А. Чехов, А. Островский, Н.В. Гоголь, А. Арбузов, А. Володин, В. Розов) и свой уникальный и неповторимый стиль. Такие исследователи как В. Я. Лакшин, Н. В. Цымбалистенко и А. Ю. Мещанский обращают внимание на большое количество реминисценций и аллюзий в его текстах на произведения Плавта, Теренция, а также библейские мотивы (пьеса «Старший сын» напрямую отсылает нас к притче о Блудном сыне).

В своем творчестве А. В. Вампилов, как и А. П. Чехов, изображал современную ему действительность. Герои его пьес формируются с помощью приема психологизма. В их образах драматург стремился показать, как именно быт накладывает свой отпечаток на их поведение и мотивацию. Тем самым можно сказать, что социальный уклад - главный критерий для характеристики персонажей.

В драматургии Вампилова отчетливо прослеживается полифонизм и один из новаторских приемов – прием монтажа (в пьесе «Утиная охота» этот способ проявляется в соединении с ретроспекцией). Герои его произведений приходят к духовному росту через свой внутренний конфликт. С. М. Козлова, обращаясь к творчеству А. П. Чехова и А. В. Вампилова, выявила сходные и различные черты в поэтике двух писателей. Первое на что она обратила внимание – это резкое сокращение объема драмы: там, где у Чехова четыре действия, Вампилову понадобилось только два. Исследователь также утверждает: «Вампилов, дитя своего рационального века, хотел бы примирить Ибсена и Чехова, повысив ибсеновскую цену человека, но значительно сократив сроки чеховской эволюции. Для Вампилова, как и для Ибсена, – природа человека представляется пластичной, податливой, но он хотел бы, как Чехов, не приспособить ее к среде, а усовершенствовать нравственно. Но в отличие от Чехова – в пределах одной жизни» [4, с. 187]. Также пьесам Вампилова присуще игровое начало.

Впервые это зафиксировала И.И. Плеханова в своей работе: «динамизм и универсальность игрового начала, пронизывающего сферу сюжета, чувств и поведения героев, речевых характеристик, текста и подтекста, обеспечивают сценичность и особую философскую глубину пьес» [7, с. 252]. А. С. Собенников считает, что одной из важнейших сюжетобразующих линий в пьесах Вампилова является мотив случая. Сам Вампилов писал: «Случай, пустяк, стечение обстоятельств иногда становятся самыми драматическими моментами в жизни человека» [2, с. 537].

В драматургии Вампилова заметно большое влияние философии русского экзистенциализма, связанного прежде всего с именем Ф. М. Достоевского. С. Р. Смирнов в своей статье «Психоэмоциональные мотивы («норма» – «здравомыслие» – «абсурд») и их место в творческом процессе А. Вампилова» обращается к непосредственным упоминаниям, скрытым цитатам и реминисценциям из Достоевского у Вампилова. «Их не так много, - утверждает автор, - но все они являются знаковыми. Два упоминания содержатся в «Записных книжках» Вампилова: «Все люди кажутся иногда самыми отвратительными типами Достоевского». И второе: «Условия для самоубийства у тебя есть. Тебе только не хватает теоретической подготовки. Читай Шопенгауэра, Достоевского, Кафку»». Перечисление этих имен в одном ряду свидетельствует о широком кругозоре Вампилова и его глубоких экзистенциальных размышлениях. Тема смерти, а если быть точными, попытка самоубийства, показана во многих произведениях драматурга. Примерами могут служить дуэль Букина и Фролова в пьесе «Прощание в июне», которая привела к выстрелу в птицу, переживания Васеньки из-за невзаимной любви к Макарьской и самая явная провокация Шаманова в разговоре с Пашкой, закончившаяся осечкой при выстреле. Наконец, неудачная попытка Зилова и удавшееся самоубийство Валентины в черновом варианте «Прошлым летом в Чулимске». Однако в отличие от других авторов, Вампилов своих персонажей не убивает: «А я вот никого не убил из своих героев, – негромко заявил Вампилов, явно довольный этим обстоятельством» [2, с. 376].

В художественном методе А. В. Вампилова мы можем увидеть черты лирической драмы, характерной для И. С. Тургенева. Оба писателя при реализации приема психологизма используют пейзажные зарисовки. В драме «Прошлым летом в Чулимске» автор описывает цветы, беспорядочно растущие прямо в траве, словно в лесу. Исследователи видят в этом душевную отчужденность персонажей и углубление их в свое внутренне «я», их эгоизм и абсолютное нежелание понимать друг друга. Помятые цветы – символ духовного обнищания героев, травмированных общественным укладом. Стремление Валентины посадить маки в палисаднике свидетельствует о ее потребности к пробуждению нравственно-духовных идеалов.

Вампилов тонко почувствовал дуальное существование мира, отметив, что люди делятся на очень бессовестных и очень простосердечных, наглых и скромных, однако отсутствуют люди нормы, с чисто положительными характеристиками. Часто его герои оказываются бессильными перед различными обстоятельствами жизни. Они чувствуют растерянность перед существующей действительностью и беспомощность в определенных ситуациях. Причем драматическое чутье Вампилова точно угадывало, что то или иное состояние, в котором пребывает герой, является всего лишь маской: бессовестность оказывается вариантом совестливости, а честность и наглость – это театральная атрибутика, которую можно снять и надеть снова. Чем искуснее социум, тем глубже чувства и переживания совестливых, тем они уязвимее. Беспомощная кротость Сарафанова делает из него святого, и стоит Бусыгину вступить в семейный клан, как он тут же превращается в любящего сына. Цинизм порождает беспомощность.

Чувства так зыбки, отношения так хрупки, что инстинктивно приходишь к выводу о взаимозависимости вульгарности общества, которое описывает Вампилов, и закономерного погружения в жанр мелодрамы.

Писатель по-другому переосмысливает некоторые драматургические клише. Например, при детальном анализе творчества Вампилова можно заметить, что однозначное деление героев на положительных и отрицательных оказывается невозможным. Стоит подчеркнуть, что иногда эти штампы используются Вампиловым для абсурдной пародии, что приводит к острой конфликтности и синтезу экстравагантности с трагичностью.

Еще одной уникальностью «театра Вампилова» является вопрос о типологии его персонажей. В литературоведении до сих пор нет четкого понимания, к какому из типов отнести персонажей его пьес. Е. Гушанская выделила «рефлексирующего» героя; С. Боровиков говорит о герое-бунтаре; тип бюрократа отмечается у Б. Сушкова; В. Соловьев находит у Вампилова героя - «праведника». Другие исследователи отмечают, что драматург вывел на театральную сцену «делового человека», образ которого продолжает традиции маленького человека А. С. Пушкина, Н. В. Гоголя и Ф. М. Достоевского. Однако уникальность творчества Вампилова как раз в том, что невозможно отнести определенного персонажа к тому или иному типу. Его герои не статичны, они постоянно, иногда незаметно для неискушенного читателя-зрителя, меняются. Порой обладая всеми характеристиками этих типажей, они в то же время не соотносятся ни с одним из них. Герои пьес Вампилова очень многогранны, подчас обладают противоречивыми качествами. Как раз поэтому так интересно наблюдать за их трансформацией, духовным становлением. Как правило, внешняя сторона жизни персонажа вполне состоятельна – он обеспечен, у него имеются друзья, работа и семья (Зилов). Однако социально-бытовая рутина, находящаяся в противоборстве с внутренним миром героя, способствует духовной смерти. Несмотря на это, финал пьесы оптимистичен – происходит нравственное перерождение персонажа, его ценностно-смысловое переосмысление.

Герой А. Вампилова не является ни городским, ни деревенским. Скорее можно сказать, что он провинциальный. В русской литературе прочно укоренилась оппозиция провинция-столица, поэтому и драматург не смог обойти ее стороной. Как правило, почти все герои Вампилова провинциалы. Исследователи театроведческого направления творчества Вампилова отмечают, что в театр драматург пришел не один. Он принес с собой предельную искренность и безмерную доброту, присущие людям периферии. При, казалось бы, внешней упрощенности его произведений, в вампиловских текстах есть та самая незаурядность, которая отличает его от всех других авторов. Жизнеописание в пьесах драматурга правдиво и реалистично.

А. В. Вампилов неустанно выискивал новые формы для воплощения своих замыслов, создавал новые и совершенствовал старые формулы построения реалистической драмы. Поэтому автор неизбежно радуется читателя-зрителя панорамностью, а порой и парадоксальностью жизнеописания, которые присущи его пьесам.

Пьесы А. Вампилова характеризуются глубоким смыслом, оригинальностью изображения и актуальностью происходящего. Вампилов мастерски пользуется необычными техниками и художественными приемами, создающими неповторимую атмосферу его произведений. Это помогает лучше выразить идеи и концепции самого автора. Такие драматические приемы как интрига, конфликт, развитие сюжета, психологический портрет персонажа неизменно присутствовали в арсенале

драматурга. Наличие в его пьесах глубоких и противоречивых персонажей делает произведения писателя сложными для восприятия, то есть не всегда его героев можно трактовать однозначно. Пьесы А. Вампилова в большинстве своем основаны на реальных событиях, что делает его драматургию правдивой и убедительной, он описывал те проблемы и явления, которые актуальны для людей в современном обществе. Драматургия Александра Вампилова отличается проникновенной искренностью, философским осмыслением и острой социальной направленностью.

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ABDULLA QAHHORNING “MAYIZ YEMAGAN XOTIN” HIKOYASINING LINGVISTIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Barcha zamonlarda ayol siymosiga, ayol xarakterini ochib berishga bag‘ishlangan asarlar yaratilgan. Bu esa ayolning jamiyat va insoniyat hayotidagi o‘rni, ayol timsolining dolzarbligidan dalolat beradi. Jamiyatda xotin-qizlarning tengligi, ozodligi uchun erkaklar bilan tengma-teng ishlashi mavzusi yorqin badiiy shaklda ochiladigan hikoyalardan biri bu Abdulla Qahhorning “Mayiz yemagan xotin” hikoyasidir. Maqolada ham inson ruhiyatining murakkabligi, o‘sha davr va jamiyat istilosi haqida, shu bilan birga til va adabiyot uyg‘unligi, hikoyada til birliklarining o‘rni, haqida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘z: frazema, urf-odat, fenomen, yo‘nalish, stil, obrazlilik, reallashuv, ironiya.

Abdulla Qahhorning “Mayiz yemagan xotin” asari oddiy, ammo chuqur ma’noli voqeani hikoya qiladi. Avvalo, ushbu asarning tili, yozilish stili haqida so‘z ochsak: ushbu asar o‘ziga xos yo‘nalishda, ayanchli voqealar, ayollarning huquq va majburiyatlari haqida “noto‘g‘ri” tasavvur va “mish-mishlar” haqida ochiq bayon etiladi. Asarning markaziy mavzusi ayollarning an’anaviy jamiyatdagi nogiron qilib qo‘yilgan mavqeyi va ko‘r-ko‘rona urf-odatlariga qattiq tanqidi, ayollar ilmsiz bo‘lishlari, jamiyatda faqatgina suyuqli ayol va ona

rolida bo'lishlari kerakligi, ayollar huquqi, xohish-istaklari, orzu-maqсадlari yo'q qilinishi kerakligi ochiqlanadi. Vaholanki, ayollar ilmsiz bo'lgan jamiyat tanazzulga yuz tutadi. Masalan, o'tmishga nazar solsak, buyuk sarkarda Amir Temur, g'azal mulkingning sultoni – Alisher Navoiy, muhaddis Imom Buxoriylarning onalari ilmli, oqila, pokdomon ayollar bo'lib, farzandlarini buyuk shaxs bo'lib yetishishi uchun ilmga burkab tarbiyalaganlar. Ilmli ona – jamiyat quroli.

Abdulla Qahhor o'z uslubi – psixologik ta'sir kuchi, oz hajm, teran va chuqur ma'no orqali jamiyatdagi noqis voqealarni yoritadi. Asardagi obrazlar ham shu yo'nalishga mos tarzda tanlanadi. Asardagi bosh qahramon – Mulla Norqo'zi. Jamiyatdagi ayollarning ilmsiz bo'lishi, o'z kasbi, mutaxassisligiga ega bo'lmasligi, fikr erkinligi, kiyinish erkinligidan mahrum holda yashashi uchun va'z o'qib yuruvchi diqqatsiz qahramon. Mulla Norqo'ziga bir so'z bilan ta'rif beradigan bo'lsak, amali ilmiga to'g'ri kelmaydigan beburd obraz. Uning ayoli esa tashqaridan qaraganda o'zini ilmli, amali ilmidan go'zal, pokdomon qilib ko'rsatuvchi, aslida esa, ichki sifatlarini “*yetti qavat parda ichiga*” yashirgan munofiq ayol obrazidir. Xuddi shunday insonlar borligi uchun ham ayollar o'z huquq va erkinliklaridan mahrum bo'layotganligini tanqid qilib ochiq tasvirlaydi. Abdulla Qahhor frazemalardan foydalanish orqali o'z asarlari va asarlaridagi qahramonlar xarakterini yoritib beradi. Masalan, Mulla Norqo'zi tilidan aytilgan: “Sotiboldining xotini dorixonada ishlaydi, har kuni mingta odam bilan javob-muomala qiladi: axir, bittasi bo'lmasa bittasi ko'z qisadi-da! Meliqo'zining xotini avtobusda konduktor, ba'zan yarim kechada keladi; ishi erta tugagan kuni ham yarim kechagacha yursa, ayshini qilsa eri bilib o'tiriptimi?” [1.86]. Ushbu satrlar orqali asosiy obraz – din ulamosining insonlar haqida yomon gumonda bo'lishi, g'iybat qilishi orqali salbiy voqeliklarni ko'rsatadi, ya'ni ilmi amaliga mos bo'lmagan xarakter egasi ekanligini, “*ko'r ko'rni qorong'uda topar*” deganlaridek, xotini ham undan qolishmasligini ko'ramiz. Uning ayoli tilidan: “Hazilingiz qursin! - dedi chiroqni pastlatayotib, - kishining imonini qochiradi. Ochilish u yoqda tursin, ochiq xotinlarning yuzini ham ko'rmayman, deb ont ichganman. Bir kuni besh-oltita ochiq xotin orasiga kirib qolib, ne vaqtgacha *ko'nglim g'ash, ta'bim kir bo'lib* yurdim”. Bu yerda qahramon o'zini juda imonli, sadoqatli yor sifatida ko'rsatadi. Ammo asar so'ngida yozuvchi uning munofiq xarakter egasi ekanligi ochib beradi. Frazemalar faqatgina asar emotsionalligini, badiiy tilini ochibgina qolmay, obrazlar xarakterini kuchaytirib ifodalash uchun xizmat qiladi.

Abdulla Qahhor asar estetikasini, emotsionalligini kuchaytirish maqsadida til birliklaridan ham unumli foydalanib alohida fenomenik asar yaratgan. Masalan, yuqorida keltirilgan asarning lingvistik tahlilini ko'rib chiqadigan bo'lsak, unda frazeologizmlardan salmoqli foydalanganligi uchun ham asarning badiiy emotsionalligi kitobxon aqlini, qalbini va butun vujudini qamrab oladi. Yozuvchi asarda quyidagi frazemalardan foydalangan:

“Mulla Norqo'zi har kuni bozordan qaytib samovarga chiqadi va ko'ngli tortgan odamlarni atrofiga to'plab, yarim kechagacha shariatdan yuz o'g'irgan xotinlar to'g'risida shunday vaysab o'tiradi” [1.88]. Ushbu gapning o'zida yozuvchi ikkita – “*yuz o'g'irmoq*” hamda “*ko'ngli tortmoq*” frazemasidan foydalanadi va bu frazemalar Shavkat Rahmatullayevning O'zbek tilining frazeologik lug'atida biror shaxs yoki voqeaga qaramaslik, yuzini burish ma'nolarini ifodalaydi [5.308]. Abdulla Qahhor esa buni parchada “vos kechish” ma'nosida qo'llaydi. “*Ko'ngli tortmoq*” iborasi esa “*yoqtirmoq*” ma'nosini anglatadi. Asarda esa “o'zi istagan, xohlagan” ma'nosini ifoda etadi. Mazkur iboralar bir gap ichida ishlatilishi bilan yozuvchining san'atkorona mahorati, teran fikrlashini yuqori saviyada ko'rsatadi.

“Bo, xudo, paranjini tashlab ko'chada yurishga yuzi chidagandan keyin uyati bormi!”. “*Yuzi chidamoq*” frazemasini esa uyat-andisha qilmoq, nomus qilmoq ma'nolarini izohlab

kelib, asarda ibo-hayo milliy qadriyatlardan biri ekanligini, bu yerda esa andisha qilish ma'nosida kelmoqda. Yozuvchi asarlarida qo'llagan frazemalar bilan hikoyaning ekspressiv bo'yoqdorligini ham oshirib, kitobxon diqqatini tortadi. Har bir parchada asar g'oyasini, xarakterini hamda yozilish uslubini ham ko'rsatib boradi. "Sotiboldining xotini dorixonada ishlaydi, har kuni mingta odam bilan javob-muomila qiladi: axir, bittasi bo'lmasa bittasi ko'z qisadi-da!" [1.89]. Avvalo, qahramon nutqini tanqid ostiga oladigan bo'lsak, Mulla Norqo'zi har bir ayollar harakatidan buzuqlik holatlarini qidiradi, hikoya orqali erkaklarning bilib-bilmay ig'vo va g'iybatlarga aralashishi, ayollarning ishlashiga bo'lgan qarshiliklar ochiq-oydin o'z aksini topadi. Ba'zi qo'shtirnoq ichidagi erkaklar ayollarning o'qimishli bo'lishiga qarshi chiqadi. Albatta, g'iybat qilish erkaklarga xos bo'lmagan eng yomon illatlardan biri hisoblanadi. Mulla Norqo'zi ayollarning paranjisi-yu, qayerda ishlash-ishlamasligini gapirar ekan, o'zining qanchalar tuban kishi ekanligini ko'rsatib beradi. Frazemaning izohiga keladigan bo'lsak, "ko'z qismoq" – "imlash", "jalb qilish" singari mazmuni anglatadi. Asarda ham aynan "imlash", "chaqirish" ma'nosini izohlaydi.

"Ochiq xotin-qizlarning har bir harakatidan mulla Norqo'zi buzuqlikka dalolat qiladigan talay belgilar topadi. "Yetti qavat parda ichida" o'tiradigan o'z xotini esa bular qarshisida ko'ziga farishta bo'lib ko'rinadi". Hikoyaning eng achinarli joyi shundaki, erkaklar birovning g'iybatini qilguncha, o'zining xotini vaqtida bu sharmandali yo'ldan qaytara olmaganidir. Agar Mulla Norqo'zi ko'chadagi xotin-qizlarni gapirguncha, o'zining xotiniga e'tiborli bo'lganda edi, asar oxirida el-yurt oldida bunday mazlum bo'lmas edi.

"Xotin chars bedanaday patillab, qochmoqchi bo'lganida yuzini karnaygulning poyasiga urib oldi. Yuzi butoqqa yomon tegdi. *Ko'ngli ozdi*". Ushbu frazema Shavkat Rahmatullayev O'zbek tilining frazeologik lug'atida "bexush bo'lmoq" deya izohlaydi [5.151]. Yozuvchi ham aynan ko'ngli aynishi, behush bo'lish holatlarini tasvirlamoqchi bo'ladi. "Umuman, yozuvchi til elementlaridan foydalanishga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Qahramonlar xarakterini ochishda ichki va tashqi nutqdan o'rinli foydalanadi. Asarda alamzadalik holatlari ham keltiriladi ya'ni Mulla Norqo'zining ayoli bilan suhbatida bu yaqqol ko'rinadi" [2.47]. Quyidagi parchada aynan frazema orqali voqea ekspressivligi oshiriladi. "Mulla Norqo'zi hazil bilan uning alamini bosmoqchi bo'ldi". "*Alamini bosmoq*" iborasi Shavkat Rahmatullayev O'zbek tilining frazeologik lug'atida "*alamini olmoq*" shaklida keltirilgan bo'lib, "kishi o'zining alamzadaligini tarqatish uchun boshqalarga zulm qilinishi" izohlanadi [5.19]. Asar tilida esa bu frazema Norqo'zining ayolining ruhiy holatini sal kuchliroq ko'rsatish uchun mohirona qo'llangan. Badiiy asarlarda, she'riyatda iboralar shu qadar muhim o'ringa egaki, asar jumllarini shunchaki boyitibgina qolmay, bir so'z bilan butun asar g'oyasini ham hikoya qiladi. Masalan, "*yuzini qora qilmoq*" iborasiga to'xtalsak, asarda bosh obraz, din ulamosi bo'lishiga qaramay "*ko'ngli qora*", "*yuzi shuvut*" obraz. "*Bir ayolning hiylasi qirq tuyaga yuk bo'lar*" deganlaridek, Mulla Norqo'zining xotini ham qirq tuya ko'tara olmaydigan hiylalar egasi. Bunga yana bir dalil ayoli tilidan aytilgan jumla: "Zerikkan bo'lsangiz, u dunyo-bu dunyo yuzimni qora qilmasdan, javobimni bera qoling...". Bu yerda keltirilgan frazema "*yuzini qora qilmoq*" ayolining yana bir hiylasi, o'zini yaxshi, oriyatli inson sifatida ko'rsatishini izohlab, obraz sifatlarini kuchaytirish uchun ishlatilgan. Yana bir jumla yuqorida aytib o'tilgan fikrlar tasdig'idir. "U bir hafta bo'yi qovog'ini ochmadi, uch kecha o'rnini boshqa solib yotdi". Bir hafta davomida "*qovog'ini ochmadi*" g'urur va hayoni saqlash maqsadida qilingan yana bir hiyla. Haqiqatan, Mulla Norqo'zi va ayoli tilidan aytilgan har bir frazema va jumlar ularning yolg'onchi, hiylakor, beburd obrazlar ekanligining isboti bo'lib kelmoqda. "Hazilingiz qursin! - dedi chiroqni pastlatayotib, - kishining *imonini qochiradi*. Ochilish u yoqda tursin, ochiq xotinlarning yuzini ham ko'rmayman, deb ont ichganman. Bir kuni besh-oltita ochiq xotin orasiga kirib

qolib, ne vaqtgacha *ko'nglim g'ash, ta'bim kir bo'lib yurdim*. Tushimda rahmatlik dadamni ko'rdim, men bilan gaplashmadilar. Gapni ko'ring-a, aytgani kishining yuzi chidamaydi". Ayol obrazining tilidan berilgan bo'lib, voqealar uning o'zini halol, pok, e'tiqodli inson sifatida ko'rsatishga urinishlari orqali yoritiladi. Aslida esa bu da'volarning ortida ikkiyuzlamachilik, riyokorlik va soxta or-nomus yashiringan. Muallif hikoyada bu holatlarni bevosita tanqid qilmaydi. Aksincha, xalqona til, yumor va badiiy kinoya orqali o'quvchini o'ylantiradi. Ayol obrazi bu yerda jamiyatdagi ma'lum bir ijtimoiy qatlamning timsoli sifatida berilgan. U o'zini "halol", "pok" deb taqdim etadi, ammo amalda bu sifatlarni o'zida namoyon qilmaydi. Bu orqali muallif gap va amal orasidagi tafovutni tanqid qiladi. Shu bilan birga, bunday obraz orqali u axloqiy qadriyatlarining jamiyatda sun'iylashib borayotganiga e'tibor qaratadi. Yozuvchining bu yerda ishlatgan tili - sodda, xalqona, ammo mazmunan juda chuqur. Oddiy so'zlar, takroriy iboralar va obrazli ifodalar orqali muallif kinoyaning ta'sirchanligini nafaqat oshiribgina qolmay, nafaqat ijtimoiy tanqid, balki o'quvchiga estetik zavq beruvchi asar sifatida ham baholanadi.

"Orqamga qaramay bir qochdim... Shariat xotinni qattiq tutish kerak deydi-yu, ammo xotinni qancha *qattiq tutsangiz*, shuncha *g'aflatda qolishingizni* poylaydi". Ushbu jumla uchinchi shaxs tomonidan aytilgan bo'lib, jamiyatda shu kabi noqis fikrlaydigan shaxslarning mavjudligi, ayollarga har sohada qarshi bo'lishlari, eng achinarlisi ayollar haqida doim noto'g'ri va noo'rin gapirishlari o'sha davrda tarqalgan vabo bo'lganligining yaqqol misolidir.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ayta olamizki, Abdulla Qahhor hikoyada oddiy va tushunarli tilni qo'llagan holda, kundalik hayotdagi voqealarni badiiy ifodalash orqali o'quvchilarga kuchli ta'sir o'tkazadi. Hikoya qisqa bo'lsa ham, uning mazmuni chuqur va ko'p qirrali. Asar o'zbek adabiyotida gender masalalarini ko'tarish va an'anaviy jamiyat qarashlarini tanqid qilish bo'yicha muhim o'rin tutadi. Hikoyada jamiyat ayollarning harakatlariga nisbatan ikkiyuzlamachi munosabatini ekani ochiqqlanadi. Mulla Norqo'zi boshqa ayollarning harakatlarini qoralaydi, lekin o'z xotinining pokdomonligi haqida haddan tashqari ishonch hosil qiladi. Bu uning qarashlari qanchalik noaniq va ikkiyuzlamachi ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Yozuvchi asar g'oyasini jamiyatdagi achinarli voqealar va adolatsizliklardan oladi.

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“OYDINDA YURGAN ODAMLAR” ASARIDAGI AYRIM FRAZELOGIZMLARNING BADIY VAZIFASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yozuvchi Tog‘ay Murodning “Oydinda yurgan odamlar” asarida qo‘llanilgan ayrim frazeologizmlarning badiiy vazifasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Frazeologizmlarning mazmun-mohiyati, asardagi o‘rni, qahramonning ruhiy holatini ifodalashdagi faol ishtiroki yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, asarda qo‘llanilgan iboralarning xalqona ruh, obrazlilik va emotsional ta‘sirchanlikni kuchaytirishdagi ahamiyati ko‘rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tog‘ay Murod, frazeologizmlar, xalq tili, badiiy ifoda, badiiy vosita, xalqona uslub.

Dunyodagi har bir millatning tili o‘zi uchun qadrlil. Til millatning boyligini, dunyoqarashini, buguni va ertasini, qadriyatlarini belgilovchi muhim vosita ekanligi hech birimizga sir emas. Binobarin, bugungi rivojlanayotgan zamonda tilning qadriyatlarini asrab-avaylash juda muhimdir. Badiiy asarlar tilimizning boyligini, xalqimizning ruhiy olamini va qadriyatlarini yanada teranroq namoyon etadi. Tilning badiiy imkoniyatlarini kengaytiruvchi muhim vositalardan biri frazeologizmlardir. Frazeologik birliklar tildagi so‘zlarning oddiy qo‘shilishidan farqli ravishda, ko‘chma ma‘no kasb etib, xalqning hayot tarzi, urf-odatlarini, madaniyati va ruhiyatini o‘zida mujassam etadi. Badiiy adabiyotda frazeologizmlar qahramonlarning ichki kechinmalari, xarakterini jonli tasvirlashda, asarga xalqona ruh bag‘ishlash, uning o‘qishlilikini oshirishda muhim vazifa bajaradi. Shu bois frazeologizmlarni bugungi kunda keng tarzda o‘rganish tilshunoslikning dolzarb masalalaridan biridir.

O‘zbek adabiyoti namoyondalarining asarlarida barqaror birikmalarning eng sara namunalarini uchratishimiz mumkin. Shunday ijodkorlardan biri o‘zbek xalqining atoqli adibi Tog‘ay Muroddir. Yozuvchi asarlarida uchraydigan har bir barqaror birlik millatimizning milliy qadriyatlari, urf-odat va an‘analari, surxon xalqining o‘ziga xos til va so‘zlashuv imkoniyatlarini ifoda etadi. Fikrimizning isboti sifatida mazkur maqolada yozuvchining “Oydinda yurgan odamlar” asarida uchraydigan ayrim frazeologizmlarning badiiy vazifasi bilan tanishib chiqamiz.

1. **Qo‘lini yuvib qo‘ltiqqa urmoq.** *“Aqalli, bir, bir yomonligimizni ko‘rsa bo‘ldi! Bizdan qo‘lini yuvib qo‘ltiqqa uradi. Biz bilan salom-alik qilmaslik payida bo‘ladi”.* Mazkur ibora “biror kimsa yoki narsadan ko‘ngli qolmoq, hafsalasi pir bo‘lmoq” kabi ma‘nolarni bildiradi va qahramonning ruhiy holatini ifodalab keladi. Asardan keltirilgan parchada ham aynan shu holat kuzatilib, qahramonning boshqalardan bo‘lar-bo‘lmas narsalar uchun ham ko‘ngli qolib ketish holati ifodalangan. Demak, mazkur ibora qahramon xafalik darajasining har qanday shakli uchun: biroz yoki tamoman ko‘ngil qolishidan qat‘iy nazar qo‘llanilishi mumkin.

2. **Ko‘ngliga olmoq.** *“Sag‘ir sertamiz bo‘ldi. Hayotda bo‘lmish ilkis qiliqlar, iring gaplarni darhol ilg‘ab oldi. Eng yomoni ko‘ngliga oldi!”.* Ushbu ibora ham “arzimagan narsaga xafa bo‘lmoq” ma‘nosini ifodalaydi hamda yuqoridagi ibora bilan sinonimlik hosil qila oladi. Iboraning emotsional bo‘yoqdorligi kuchli. U nafaqat ma‘noni, balki milliy mentalitetni ham aks ettiradi, chunki barchamizga ma‘lumki o‘zbek xalqida ko‘ngil tushunchasi juda keng ma‘no ifodalaydi. U mehr, or, hayo, g‘urur, sevgi kabi tuyg‘ular markazida turadi kishining his-tuyg‘u va kechinmalari manbayi; yurak, qalb, dil[1, 864-b]. O‘zbek tilida mazkur so‘z ishtirok etgan iboralar juda ko‘p uchraydi. Ko‘ngliga qo‘l solmoq, ko‘ngil bermoq, ko‘ngliga olmoq, ko‘nglida kiri yo‘q, ko‘ngli to‘q, ko‘ngli ketmoq kabi va boshqa iboralar shular jumlasidandir.

3. **Ko‘ngliga qo‘l solmoq.** *“Keyin qaynisinglisi ko‘ngliga qo‘l soldi: -Sen nima deysan?”.* “Ko‘ngliga qo‘l solmoq” iborasi “kimningdir eng yashirin fikr-o‘yini bilishga harakat qilmoq” ma‘nosini bildiradi va “yuragiga qo‘l solmoq” iborasi bilan sinonimlik hosil

qiladi. Asarda bu ibora qahramonning ichki sezgirligini, atrofdagilarning ruhiy holati va ichki kechinmalarini bilishga bo'lgan intilishini ifodalash uchun qo'llanilgan. Ushbu ibora fraziologik birlik sifatida o'zbek tilshunosligida muhim ahamiyatga ega.

4. **Cho'k tushmoq.** *“Kelin akasi domla qoshiga cho'k tushdi”*. Mazkur birikma ham fe'lli birikma sifatida, ham ibora sifatida qo'llanilib keladi. Agar fe'lli birikma vazifasida kelsa, “suvga cho'kmoq, g'arq bo'lmoq” ma'nolarini ifodalaydi. Birikmaning o'zagi bo'lgan “cho'kmoq” so'zi cho'kish, g'arq bo'lish holatini ifodalaydi[2, elektron manba]. Masalan: “kema cho'k tushdi”. Ibora sifatida kelganida esa “o'tirmoq”, “tizzalamoq” ma'nolarida ishlatiladi.

5. **Mijja qoqmoq.** *“Momolar mijja qoqmadi. Kuyov-qayliqni qo'riqlab o'tirdi”*. “Mijja qoqmoq” iborasi o'zbek tilshunosligi o'quvchilariga juda yaxshi tanish: “uxlamaslik”, “ko'zini ham yummaslik” ma'nolarini bildiradi. Ushbu ibora orqali yozuvchi xalqona nutq, millatning qadriyatlarini ifodalab kelgan va asarning hissiy ta'sirchanligini kuchaytirgan.

6. **Oyoq ilmoq.** *“Sen gapir, qirdan qaytib, zardolilar ostida oyoq ilganmizni, men senga zardoli terib berganimni”*. Mazkur ibora “to'xtamoq” (yo'ldan) ma'nosini ifodalaydi[3, elektron manba]. Jumlada bu ibora qahramonlarning o'tgan shirin onlarini, sokin, samimiy lahzalarni, ikki qalbning sof muhabbatga yo'g'rilgan damlarini eslash holatini ifodalashga xizmat qilgan va yozuvchining so'z qo'llash mahoratini yana bir bor isbotlagan.

7. **Yuragini hovuchlamoq.** *“Qoplon yuragini hovuchladi. –Yo pirim-e, yo pirim-e, -deya pichirladi”*. “Yuragini hovuchlamoq” iborasi asarda “biror hodisa yoki voqea yuz berishida qo'rqqan holda yuragi siqilmoq”, “ich-ichidan xavotir va hayajonni his etmoq” ma'nosida qo'llangan. Bu frazeologizm qahramonning ichki kechinmalarini, ruhiy beqarorlik va qo'rquv holatini jonli ifodalash uchun xizmat qiladi.

8. **Yelkasidan nafas olmoq.** *“Ana shunda Qoplon yelkasidan nafas oldi. Bo'g'zidagi holvani yutdi, og'zidagi holvani chaynadi”*. Ushbu ibora o'zbek frazeologizmlarining naqadar rang-barang ekanligiga yana bir isbotdir. Ibora “yengillashmoq”, “ko'ngli joyiga tushmoq”, “yelkasidan tog' ag'darilgandek bo'lmoq” ma'nolarini ifodalaydi. Asardagi jumlada esa qahramonning og'ir kechinmadan keyingi ruhiy yengillikni his etishini ifodalab bergan.

9. **Ko'z solmoq.** *“Xursandboy davraga ko'z soldi. Ayollar orasida mung'ayib o'tirmish Oymomoni ko'rib qoldi”*. Mazkur ibora “qaramoq”, “nazar tashlamoq” ma'nolarini ifodalaydi. Asarda bu frazeologizm biror narsa yoki shaxsga e'tibor qaratish, uni kuzatish yoki kimnidir qidirish ma'nolarida qo'llanilgan.

10. **Yuragini yormoq.** *“Sardor qiz bolani bir mushtladi. O'l-a, yuragimni yordingku! – dedi”*. “Yuragini yormoq” iborasi o'zbek tilshunosligida bir nechta ma'nolarni ifodalaydi. Masalan, “birovni qattiq qo'rqitmoq, cho'chitmoq” yoki “dilidagini ma'lum qilmoq, aytmoq” kabi. Asardagi jumlada esa birinchi ma'noda, ya'ni qo'rqitmoq ma'nosida qo'llanilib kelgan.

Har bir yozuvchining o'ziga xos yozish uslubi bor. Ayniqsa, yozuvchi Tog'ay Murodning ijodida hech bir ijodkor asarida uchramaydigan unsurlar talaygina. Yozuvchi ijodida surxon xalqining o'ziga xos so'zlashuv uslubi, qadriyat va an'analari namoyon bo'ladi. Shuningdek, yozuvchi asarlarida dialektlar, xalqona ifodalar, jumladan frazeologizmlar muhim badiiy vosita sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Adib ularni o'z asarlarida xalq tili ruhiga xos tabiiylik bilan qo'llaydi. “Oydinda yurgan odamlar” asarida uchraydigan iboralar nafaqat til boyligini, balki asar qahramonlarining ichki kechinmalari, ruhiy holati kabilarni chuqur ifodalashga ham xizmat qiladi. Har bir frazeologizm o'ziga xos vazifa bajarib, asarning hissiy ta'sirchanligini oshiradi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, Tog'ay Murod xalq tili boylıklaridan mohirona foydalangan holda o'ziga xos uslub yaratgan yozuvchidir.

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СКАЗКИ О ЖИВОТНЫХ, ИХ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И РАЗНОВИДНОСТИ.

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются особенности и разновидности русских народных сказок о животных, их структура и значение в системе фольклора. На основе трудов В.Я. Проппа, Э.В. Померанцевой, В.П. Аникина, О.М. Ивановой-Казас и Е.А. Костюхина анализируются типологические особенности сказок данного жанра и раскрывается роль животных как центральных персонажей повествования. Подчеркивается, что в сказках животные выступают олицетворением человеческих качеств и взаимоотношений, являясь носителями моральных и социальных смыслов. Особое внимание уделяется символике образов волка и лисы, которые воплощают противоположные стороны человеческой природы: силу и жестокость с одной стороны, и хитрость, смекалку и коварство - с другой. Делается вывод о том, что сказки о животных не только отражают народное мировоззрение, но и выполняют важную воспитательную функцию, формируя представления о добре и зле, справедливости и морали.

Ключевые слова: русская народная сказка, сказки о животных, фольклор, В.Я. Пропп, типология, символика животных, волк, лиса, человеческие качества, нравственное воспитание.

На протяжении многих веков, в процессе становления нынешних образов животных в русских народных сказках, создавалась литература, которая исследовала и описывала фольклорные особенности героев сказок различных областей, стран и т.п.

В таких работах В.Я.Проппа как «Исторические корни волшебной сказки», «Русская сказка» и «Морфология волшебной сказки», Э.В. Померанцевой «Судьбы русской сказки», В.П. Аникина «Русская народная сказка» дается представление о строении сказки, о её видах, о большом количестве разных типов героев сказки. Книги О.М. Ивановой-Казас «Мифологическая зоология» (словарь) и Е.А. Костюхина «Типы и формы животного эпоса» помогают подробно рассмотреть наиболее известных героев сказок о животных и создать их собирательный образ на основе сравнительного анализа данных героев и их действий.

Героями сказок очень часто становятся животные, олицетворяющие собой людей с различными характерами. Рассмотрению таких персонажей уделяется достаточно внимания, но литературы, объясняющей роль их существования в сказках о животных недостаточно, что связано с актуальностью темы этой работы.

Выбор указанной литературы обусловлен тем, что в русских народных сказках о животных особенно ярко проявляются характеры животных героев и их черты.

А такие книги, как А.Н. Афанасьевой «Народные русские сказки: полное издание в одном томе», «Сказки о животных», «Сказки о зайцах», «Сказки про лису и волка» дают полное представление о героях сказок о животных, описывают их черты характера, внешний вид и поступки.

В сказках о животных прослеживаются определенные характеры в разных временных рамках. Поэтому одним из важнейших вопросов является проблема дифференциации сказок о животных и сказок других жанров, в которых животные принимают участие.

Ключ к решению данной проблемы дает определение сказок о животных, предложенное В.Я. Проппом: «Под сказками о животных будут подразумеваться такие сказки, в которых животное является основным объектом или субъектом повествования. По этому признаку сказки о животных могут быть отличаемы от других, где животные играют лишь вспомогательную роль и не являются героями повествования».

К сказкам о животных, безусловно, относятся сказки, где действуют одни только звери («Лиса и журавль», «Лиса, заяц и петух», «Лиса-повитуха», «Лиса и дрозд», «Волк-дурень» и т.д.). Из сказок о взаимоотношениях человека и животных к этому жанру нужно отнести те, в которых звери являются главными героями, а люди – объектами их действия и повествование в которых ведется с точки зрения зверей, а не человека («Волк у проруби», «Собака и волк», «Мужик, медведь и лиса» и т.п.).

Сказки о животных мало похожи на рассказы из жизни животных. Животные в сказках лишь до некоторой степени действуют в согласии со своей природой, и в гораздо большей мере выступают носителями того или иного характера и производителями тех или иных действий, которые должны быть отнесены прежде всего к человеку. Поэтому мир зверей в сказках дополнен человеческим воображением, он является формой выражения мыслей и чувств человека, его взглядов на жизнь.

Животные, которые говорят, рассуждают и ведут себя, как люди, – лишь поэтическая условность: «Приключения животных спроецированы на людскую жизнь – и человеческим смыслом они-то и интересны». Отсюда основные темы русских сказок о животных – человеческие характеры, достоинства и пороки людей, типы человеческих взаимоотношений в быту, в обществе, иногда эти образы даже выглядят сатирически.

Большинство исследователей отмечают проблему классификации сказок о животных в связи с их разнообразием. О сложности типологизации сказок о животных писал В.Я. Пропп, отмечая следующие разновидности: сказки о животных («Теремок», «Колобок», «Петушок и бобовое зернышко» и т.п.); сказки о животных, близкие по своей структуре к волшебным («Волк и семеро козлят», «Кот, петух и лиса» и др.); сказки о животных, близкие по своему строю к басне («Волк и лиса»); сказки о животных, приближающиеся к литературным произведениям и имеющие форму политического памфлета («Повесть о Ерше Ершовиче»).

В народных сказках волк и лиса часто выступают как противоположные персонажи, символизирующие разные стороны человеческой природы. Образ волка в сказках традиционно ассоциируется с силой, жестокостью и агрессией. Он часто является врагом и символизирует угрозу для слабых и беззащитных. Например, в сказке «Волк и семеро козлят» волк является злодеем, стремящимся поглотить козлят. Его хищность и агрессия становятся причиной его неудачи, так как он не смог обмануть мать козлят, что символизирует победу добрых сил над злом.

В отличие от волка, лиса изображается как хитрая, мудрая и смекалистая героиня. В сказках лиса часто использует свои умственные способности для достижения целей. Например, в сказке «Лиса и журавль» лиса обманывает журавля, подавая ему еду в тарелке с плоским дном, так что журавль не может есть. Этот образ олицетворяет умение выходить из трудных ситуаций, но также и коварство.

Таким образом, в народных сказках волк и лиса представлены как символы разных человеческих качеств. Волк - это сила, жестокость и насилие, а лиса - хитрость, ловкость и коварство. Эти образы учат различать добро и зло, мудрость и глупость, и дают важные нравственные уроки для слушателей.

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SA`DULLA HAKIM GUMANIZMI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zabardast shoir, publisist Sa`dulla Hakim ijodining o`ziga xos tomonlari, publisistik asarlari, dostonlari va bir qator she`rlarining tahlillari haqida ayrim mulohazalar keltiriladi. Sa`dulla Hakimning she`rlaridagi soddalik, xalqchilik, so`z ohangi, tabiat manzaralari, tug`ilib o`sgan qishlog`ining so`lim tabiati, bolaligi o`tgan go`shalari haqida bir qator fikrlar yuritiladi.

Kalit so`zlar: she`riyat, gumanizm, tasvirlash, xalqona, zamonaviy, vatan, she`r, shoir.

Sa`dulla Hakim 1951-yil 25-martda Jizzax viloyatining Garasha qishlog`ida tavallud topgan. Uning bolaligi, yoshligi so`lim Garasha qishlog`ida, tog`lar bag`rida o`tdi. Sa`dulla Hakimdagi shoirona qalb, undagi iste`dod bolaligidan namoyon bo`la boshlagan. Sa`dulla Hakimning ilk she`riy to`plami "Hamal tonglari" nomi bilan 1981-yilda chop etilgan. Shundan keyin "Sen kutgan bahor", "Yoz oqshomi", "Ona so`z", "Saylanma", "Ko`ngil yuzi" kabi she`riy to`plamlari nashr etilgan. "Esimda qolgan kunlar", "Atom qariga sayohat" kabi publistik asarlari ham bor. Uning she`rlarini o`qir ekansiz, Vatanimizni yanada ko`proq seva boshlaysiz, Garasha tog`laridagi toza havoni, soylardagi sharqiroq suvlarni his etasiz. Shoirning eng go`zal tashbehlari, kuzatuvlari asosidagi hikmatli fikrlari tabiat bilan bog`liq. Shoir Nurota tog`lari, Garasha qishlog`ini ta`riflar ekan, mehri iyib "Bulutini-qalpoq, qorini-chopon, yomg`irni-ko`ylak qilib kiyganman" –deydi. Yana bir go`zal ta`rifga qarang:

"Olmalar lablarin qirmizga bo`ylab,

Yaproq durrasidan mo`ralab boqar". [1,15-b.]

Shoir she`rlaridagi bu go`zal tasvirlar shunchaki badiiy topilmalar uchun emas. Bunda shoirning tabiatga muhabbati jilvalanib, sezilib turadi. Shoirning "Garashaliklar qo`shig`i", "Oq qoya guli", "Jiyda pishig`i" she`rlarida ona tabiatga, Ona Vatanga muhabbati yaqqol sezilib turadi.

Tuproq nur sochib yotar,

*Tovlanar soy toshlari
Jiydalar burqsib tutar,
Yer qizigan chog`lari.
Tunda osmon yelmoy separ,
Gugurt chaqar sarsari.
Jiydalar tutab yotar
Gullar yongan chog`lari.
Yulduzlar – tutantiriq,
Kuz oyni yoqqan chog`lari,
Porlab ketar shamolda*

Qip – qizil chog`li shoxlar! [2,60-b.]

Jiyda pishig`i mavsumini ko`z oldimizga keltiradigan bo`lsak, quyoshli O`zbekistonimizda tuproqning nur sochib yotishi, quyosh nurlarida soydagi toshlarning tovlanishi hayolimizga keladi. Tunda osmon yelmay separ va sarsari gugurt chaqadi. Kuz yulduzlarni tutantiriq qilib, Oyni yoqqan chog`larida kuz gullari yonayotgandek tuyuladi. Har shamol ko`tarilganda, jiydaning shoxlari silkiganda jiydaning pishgan mevalari ko`rinadi. Shoir she`rda jiyda pishig`i vaqtini betakror tasvirlaydi.

Shoirning “Garashaliklar qo`shig`i” she`rida Vatanga, onaga, inson qadriga bo`lgan tuyg`ularni yaqqol ko`rish mumkin. Sa`dulla Hakimning ushbu she`ridagi “Yurt qadriga yetmaganni chaqmoq ursin” misrasida ona Vatanning qadriga yetmaganlarga, Vatan uchun yonib kuymaganlarga murojaatini ko`rish mumkin.

Shoir “Umrim mazmuni” she`rida shunday yozadi:

*Vatanim – nur o`pgan muqaddas kenglik,
Kengliksiz yasholmasman.
Shodligim – ilm va mehnatda tenglik,
Tengsizlik yasholmasman.
Qudratim – toshda gul undirgan elim,
Elimsiz yasholmasman.*

Elini o`z qudratining manbai deb uqqan shoir, vatanni nur o`pgan kenglik deb bilarkan, shularsiz hayot hayot emasligini his qiladi. [3,7-b.]

*Bir qo`shiq bor – qo`shiqlarning sarasi,
Shu qo`shiqni aytmoqchiman,
Qalbim shunga undaydi.
Yurt madhidan boshlanib u,
Yurt madhida tugaydi.*

Sa`dulla Hakim ijodini o`qib, o`rganar ekansiz tabiatga, ona Vatanga, yor-birodarlarga jo`shqin tuyg`ularni his eta boshlaysiz. Shoirning she`rlari, dostonlari yuqorida aytganimizdek xalqona, sodda, yosh-u qari birdek tushunadigan qilib yozilgan. Sa`dulla Hakim ijodi haqida xalq shoiri Abdulla Oripov, Jumaniyoz Jabborov, Mahmud Toir, O`tkir Rahmat, Uyg`un Ro`ziyev, Abdunabi Boyqo`ziyev, Oygul Suyundikova, Farog`at Xudoyqulova kabi elimizning taniqli shoir va yozuvchilari Ibrohim G`afurov, Qozoqboy Yo`ldosh, Najmiddin Komilov, Saydi Umirov, Ahmad Otaboy, To`lqin Eshbek, Xolmurod Salimov, Dilmurod Xoldorov kabi olimlar maqolalar yozganlar.

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ФЭНТЕЗИ СЕГОДНЯ ПОПУЛЯРНОСТЬ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ВЛИЯНИЕ ЖАНРА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается феномен популярности жанра фэнтези в современной литературе и культуре. Автор анализирует его историческое развитие, ключевые особенности и влияние на мировоззрение подростков. Особое внимание уделяется произведениям Дж. Роулинг и С. Майер, ставшим символами массовой культуры. Исследуется роль фэнтези в формировании духовных и эстетических ценностей молодёжи.

Ключевые слова: фэнтези, молодёжная литература, современная культура, влияние, развитие жанра.

С самого детства я люблю читать сказки. Мне нравилось мечтать, фантазировать, погружаться в мир волшебства и приключений. Это приносило мне массу удовольствия, но я выросла, и сказки были заменены чудесным жанром фэнтези. Помимо захватывающего сюжета, который богат приключениями и волшебством, произведения в жанре фэнтези всегда имеют философский подтекст, будят воображение[1].

Жанр фэнтези сложился в литературе в прошлом веке, но свое начало берет с древних времен и очень тесно связан с культурными традициями, обычаями народов, которые нашли отражение в мифах, преданиях, сказках. Считается, что предыстория этого жанра началась с рыцарских романов эпохи Средневековья. Их действие разворачивалось в историческом времени, но происходят они на условном "феерическом" пространстве, где настоящая, подлинная география, временное пространство, границы не важны. Обычно это было некое королевство, где рыцари силой, смелостью, смекалкой противостоят колдунам и чародеям, чудовищам, великанам. В рыцарских романах стали зарождаться шаблоны, традиции современного фэнтези. В них впервые появляется образ идеального Светлого Королевства, ведущего ожесточенную борьбу, порой бесконечную, с могучими силами Тьмы, Зла[2].

Несмотря на большое количество разнообразных писателей, основоположником жанра фэнтези, в современном понимании, до сих пор традиционно считается Джон Рональд Руэл Толкин (1892-1973) - английский писатель, литературовед. Мировую известность ему принесла эпопея о "Средиземье": "Хоббит, или Туда и обратно" (1937), "Властелин колец" (1954-1955) и "Сильмариллион" (изданный сыном Толкина в 1977). Сам Толкин определял жанр своих произведений о Средиземье как "фэери" (от англ. fairy - сказочный, волшебный). Однако принципиальное отличие этого жанра от сказок заключается в том, что все чудеса имеют закономерный и вполне объяснимый характер.

Фэнтези-произведения - это всегда остросюжетная история, которая увлекает читателя в новый, волшебный мир.

Сегодня фэнтези стало общепринятой частью поп-культуры, отношение к жанру более уважительное. Даже взрослые люди, далёкие от «гиковской» субкультуры, читают фэнтези-романы, рассматривая их как литературу для отдыха и размышлений.

Объединение фэнтезийных сюжетов с элементами других жанров. Например, существует городское фэнтези, где герой-детектив расследует магические

преступления, или фэнтези-детективы, сочетающие логику расследования с волшебными реалиями. Также набирает популярность «боевое фэнтези» - книги, где упор сделан на непрерывный экшен, сражения, погони.

Развитие поджанров, например, романтического фэнтези, где на первый план выходят любовные линии и отношения между героями. Отдельно выделяют популярный сегмент «академка» - истории про магические академии, колледжи или университеты, где учатся молодые маги.

Влияние на другие сферы, в частности на видеоигры. Существует большое количество экшен-игр в жанре фэнтези, фэнтези-стратегии и фэнтези-приключенческие игры. Дальше на рассмотрение мы берем «Гарри Поттера». История о молодом волшебнике, который сражается с силами зла, покорила миллионы сердец читателей. Цикл романов из семи книг пользуется популярностью не только у детей и подростков, но и у взрослой аудитории. Свою историю «Гарри Поттер» начинает в июне 1997 года, когда была опубликована первая книга Джоан Кэтлин Роулинг - «Гарри Поттер и философский камень». Произведение достаточно быстро становится популярным, тиражи растут в геометрической прогрессии. Начиная с четвертой части - «Кубка Огня», все последующие книги бьют мировые рекорды по продажам. Книги становятся бестселлерами и являются ими по сей день. Сегодня мы имеем целое поколение, которое выросло вместе с Гарри Поттером. На наших глазах Поттер превратился в отдельный культурный феномен. Книги переведены на 67 языков и количество проданных экземпляров перевалило за полмиллиарда[3].

Эта история о мальчике - Гарри, который в очень раннем возрасте лишился своих родителей, по вине главного антагониста истории - Лорда Волан - де-Морта. Потеряв колоссально много своих сил на убийство молодой семьи, темный лорд вынужден много лет скрываться от мира, в надежде, что однажды вся былая мощь вернется к нему. В первых трех книгах Гарри удачно мешает самому опасному волшебнику всех времен обрести тело и силу, но в четвертой книге Волан-де-Морт возвращает себе все свое могущество. Цель жизни главного героя - это спасти мир от хаоса и страданий, которые несет с собой злодей. При помощи и поддержке своих друзей, наставников и всех небезразличных волшебников, неся при этом колоссальные потери, Гарри Поттер выигрывает эту войну. Естественно - это опять же очень интересный сюжет. Целый новый мир, новый лексикон, который на сегодняшний день уже привычен очень многим людям, огромное количество сказочных, магических животных, и сила, которая отличает магов от маглов (обычных людей). Чтение «Гарри Поттера» - это очень приятный, не напрягающий, но при этом интересный побег от реальности, который привлекателен для многих возрастных групп. Дети, читая Поттера, восхищаются именно силой героев - как физическим превосходством (сила от обладания волшебными предметами, существами), так и силой их духа, решительностью, которой порой не хватает им в реальной жизни. Для более взрослых людей - это способ ненадолго уйти от ежедневных проблем, забот и ответственности, ненадолго забыться и вернуться в детство. В этой истории достаточно четко понятно, где добро, а где зло. Редко, когда герои кардинально меняются, переходя из одной категории в другую. Но при этом до последней книги так же присутствует интрига, подогревается интерес читателей неожиданными поворотами в истории. (как пример можно взять факт того, что Гарри Поттер являлся одним из семи крестажей - частичкой души Волан-де-Морта).

И последним разберем серию романов американской писательницы Стефани Майер - «Сумерки». Первая из четырех книг - «Сумерки» была выпущена осенью 2005 года. Книга моментально стала бестселлером[4]. На волне успеха, в последующие

несколько лет Майер выпустила еще три книги, которые не уступали популярности друг другу.

История любви самой обычной девушки - подростка Беллы и вампира Эдварда в первую очередь была предназначена для подростковой аудитории. Но, как это часто бывает, читательская публика данных произведений вышла за пределы изначально поставленных рамок.

Истории о вампирах не новы: леденящий кровь Носферату, жуткий Дракула, если брать более современные истории, то вампиры из Блейда, которых ненавидишь с самого начала повествования. «Сумерки» - это совсем новый формат вампиров. Тут главный акцент делается уже не на их безграничной силе или же жуткой сущности, а на их безупречной внешности. Главный герой - это молодой парень, с идеальной внешностью, загадочным характером, который отличается от всех окружающих. И тот факт, что влюбляется он в самую заурядную девушку, является одной из главных причин популярности саги. Девочки - подростки, для которых писались эти книги, да и девушки, женщины постарше, часто проецируют данную ситуацию на себя: «А вот что если бы это была я...». Несложный язык, которым написаны книги, эпичность некоторых действий, романтичность героев, внешний лоск всего, что связано с этим миром - это все является рецептом огромного успеха данной «Саги»[5].

Моя гипотеза о том, что жанр фэнтези является популярной литературой для подростков и что чтение фэнтези формирует активную, творческую, гармонически развитую личность, подтвердилась полностью. Такой вывод я сделала на основе анкетирования, опроса пятиклассников, анализа статей на данную тему, беседы со школьным психологом.

С чтением всегда было связано духовное развитие человечества. Однако последние годы характеризуются резким падением интереса к печатному слову. Время досуга современный подросток всё чаще проводит перед телевизором или компьютером. И всё же, как я это выяснила, есть ещё подростки, которые с удовольствием читают художественную литературу.

Современные романтически настроенные подростки увлекаются жанром фэнтези. В ходе общения со сверстниками было выяснено, что чтение этих книг увлекает романтикой открытий неизведанного и необычайного, расширяет кругозор, развивает творческую фантазию и воображение. Основная черта фэнтези схватывается детьми очень чутко – естественность чуда, размытость границ между мирами, возможность невозможного.

В большинстве случаев опыт и знание жизни подросток черпает именно из книг. Вместившая в себя лучшие традиции классической литературы и фольклорную мудрость, фэнтези сегодня взяло на себя роль, которую ранее успешно выполняла реалистическая, классическая литература - воспитание личности.

Не стоит игнорировать предпочтения молодёжи. Часто бывает, что «поп-литература» становится единственным средством найти взаимопонимание между поколениями. Фэнтези – часть «поп - литературы», которая имеет эстетически достойные произведения, имеющие завидную и неугасающую популярность среди подростков.

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ULUG‘BEK HAMDAMNING “MUVOZANAT” ROMANI VA UNDAGI OBRAZLARNING O‘ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Ulug‘bek Hamdamning “Muvozanat” romani va undagi obrazlar, ularning qarashlari va ruhiy holatlarini, ichki konfliktlarini, shuningdek, ilk mustaqillik davridagi o‘zgarishlar hamda o‘sha paytdagi insonlar holatini ifodalashdagi yozuvchining o‘ziga xos jihatlari haqida so‘z boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: realizm, konflikt, obraz, ruhiy holat, davr, ramziy ma’no.

Bugungi kunda adabiyot olamida Ulug‘bek Hamdamning alohida o‘rni bor. Adib o‘zining chuqur ma’noli asarlari bilan xalq orasida shuhrat va mehr qozongan. Uning “Muvozanat”, “Isyon va itoat”, “Sabo va Samandar”, “Ota” kabi romanlari, “Tangriga eltuvchi isyon”, “Atirgul”, “Seni kutdim” kabi she’riy to‘plamlari adabiyotimizning noyob durdonalari safiga kirgan. Uning ko‘plab asarlari xalqimiz va chet el kitobsevarlari qalbidan munosib o‘rin egallashga ulgurgan. Xususan, “Isyon va itoat” romani, “Yolg‘izlik” qissasi, ko‘plab she’r va hikoyalari ruschaga tarjima qilingan. Ijodkorning “Muvozanat” va “Tosh” kabi roman hamda hikoyalari Amerikada alohida e’tirof etilgan.

Adibning har bir asari o‘ziga xos chuqur falsafiy ma’noga ega bo‘lgani kabi “Muvozanat” romani ham g‘oyat serma’no. “Muvozanat” mohiyatiga ko‘ra realistik roman hisoblanadi. Yozuvchi unda ilk mustaqillik davridagi o‘zgarishlar, qiyinchiliklar va insonlar ruhiy holatini mohirlik bilan ifodalagan.

“Muvozanat” haqida ko‘plab ijodkorlar fikr va mulohazalarini bildirib o‘tishgan, xususan, Ozod Sharafiddinov “Romanni o‘qib chiqar ekanman, bugungi kun odamini tasvirlashda realizmning hali ochilmagan imkoniyatlari ko‘p ekaniga imon keltirdim”, - deydi [1,24].

Adib asarda yaqin o‘tmish, doimiy odatlangan turmushdagi o‘zgarishlar, yangi prinsiplar insonlar ongi va ruhiyatida kuchli o‘zgarishlar yasaganini, ichki va tashqi kelishmovchiliklar yuzasidan kelib chiqqan muvozanatsizlik holatlarini qalamga olgan. G‘oyat murakkab tanlangan mavzu mohiyati, asar syujeti va g‘oyasi roman nomining o‘zidanoq ko‘zga tashlanadi.

Albatta, asar mazmunida inson, ya’ni Yusufning taqdiri, uning o‘y-kechinmalari yotadi. Kitobxon qahramon bilan birga voqealar rivojida qatnashadi, kuzatadi, muammolar ildizi qayerdan paydo bo‘lganini topishga intiladi, birga yig‘laydi, kuladi, o‘sha davr muhitini ko‘z oldida paydo qilishga urinadi. Yozuvchining maqsadi ham aynan Yusuf va uning atrofidagi odamlar vositasida o‘sha davrni gavdalantirish bo‘lgan, desak mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi.

Yusuf- o‘z fikriga va zamonaviy qarashlarga ega shaxs, halol yigit. O‘z kasbini yaxshi ko‘radigan va uni sidqidildan bajaradigan inson. Ma’rifatli bo‘lgani uchun mustaqillik nima-yu qaramlik nima juda yaxshi biladi. Yusuf har doim halol yashashga intiladi, o‘z qadriyatlariga sodiq qolishga, atrofida sodir bo‘layotgan voqea-hodisalarni tushunishga va

ularni hal etishga, to'g'ri yo'ldan borishga urinadi. Ko'pchilik odamlar singari Yusuf ham mustaqillikning dastlabki bosqichlarida- "Bozor iqtisodiyoti"ga o'tish davri girdoblarida ancha dovdirab, muvozanatni yo'qotib qo'yadi. Yozuvchi esa bu holatni "Yusufning ichida nimadir qarsillab sindi" deya ta'riflaydi. U doim ishongan, qadrlagan muhabbat, do'stlik, birdamlik kabi oliy tuyg'ular puch bo'lib chiqadi, hammadan hafsalasi pir bo'ladi. Ayoli bilan ajrashadi, do'stlari o'z manfaatlari yo'lidan ketib Yusufni butunlay unutadi.

Yuqorida Yusuf atrofida bo'layotgan voqealarni tushunishga harakat qiladi dedik, bunga misol qilib qahramonning do'stlari haqidagi quyidagi fikrlarini olishimiz mumkin: "Axir, kechagina- rahbar lavozimida ishlab yurganida Said qanaqa edi, bugun- ishdan ketib, uyda o'z qismati bilan o'zi yolg'iz qolganda qanday? Kecha uning yuzlaridan, gap- so'zi-yu butun harakatlaridan kuch yog'ilardi. O'zini juda azim va arzigulik maqsadga bag'ishlagani hamda o'sha yo'lda dadil qadam bosayotgani sezilib turardi. Erishga muvaffaqiyatlari shu qadar zo'r ediki, esiga do'stlik... Yusuf ham kelmasdi. Bugun-chi? Bugun u hammasidan mosuvo etildi va ilgorigi g'ayratidan, ko'zda chaqnab turgan olovdan asar ham qolmadi: cho'kdi-ketdi. Demakki, u o'zini tutib turgan maqsad-u manfaatidan, ko'pchilik bilan bir deb his qilish yuksakligidan judo bo'lib, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy jihatdan yakkalanib qolgan..."[2, 252].

"Mirazim- chi? Bolalikning barcha havaslari ro'yobga chiqib, yuragi huvillab qolgan Mirazim! Orzularining birontasiga ham yetolmagan Amir bu yoqda aqldan ozar bo'lsa, u yonda barcha niyatlari amalga oshgan Mirazim o'zini bosh- keti yo'q sahroga chiqib qolgandek his etmadimi? Etdi. Xo'sh, nega? Axir, Mirazim hamma orzusiga erishdiku?!...Har ikkala holda ham inson yakkalanib qolmadimi?.." [2,253]

Darhaqiqat, Yusuf, Said, Mirazim talabalik yillarida juda qalin do'stlar edi, Yusuf ularning "boshi", eng aqllisi va ishbilarmoni edi. Ular hamma narsani birga baham ko'rardilar, birgalikda muammolarni hal qilardilar. Keyinchalik, yillar o'tgach, hamma o'z yo'lidan ketdi, to'g'rirog'i, Yusufning ikkala do'sti ham zamon po'rtanalarida qulab ketmaslik uchun o'zlarini har ko'yga soldilar va hammasining yo'llari ayro tushdi. Said katta lavozimda ishlash uchun hamma narsadan voz kechgan bo'lsa, Mirazim ota kasbi tadbirkorlikni davom ettirib, butun dunyoni unutdi...

Asarda Yusufning akasi, Amir obrazi ham alohida ta'riflashga arzigulik personaj. U asarda berilgan eng ta'sirli obraz. Amir hech qaysi orzusi amalga oshmagan, umidlari puchga chiqqan va bu alamlar kelgusi hayotida achchiq iz qoldirib, natijada telbaga aylangan inson. U dinga shu darajada kirishganki, dunyoni tamoman unutgan, dunyo va din orasidagi muvozanatni yo'qotgan. U aqlan va jismonan sog' bo'lishiga qaramay jinnixonaga tashlanadi, o'zini telbaday tutishga majbur bo'ladi, jinnilar qo'lida pati yulingan musicha qiyofasida ramziy ma'noda o'zini ko'radi.

Asardagi Sodiq obrazi- Yusufning bolalikdagi do'sti- ikki muhitdan birini tanlolmay arosatda qolgan odam. U mustaqillikdan avvalgi zamon yaxshimidi yo hozirgi zamon yaxshimi- farqlay olmaydi. Eski tuzumni maqtay desa, ma'naviy jihatdan juda qiynaladi, mustaqillikni maqtay desa, moddiy jihatdan qiynaladi. Fikrlariga oydinlik kiritish uchun doim Yusufni so'roq qiladi, Yusuf esa nima bo'lishidan qat'i nazar mustaqillikni afzal ko'radi.

Asardagi Zahro obrazi sadoqat va xiyonat o'rtasida arosatda qolgan obraz sanaladi. Unda hamma narsa bor, faqat ozodlik, erkinlik yo'q. U o'qigan, ilimli ayol bo'lishiga qaramay uyda tutqun kabi o'tirishga majbur insonlarning timsoli sifatida tasvirlangan. Mirazim oilaga egalik tushunchasini noto'g'ri tushungani uchun Zahro xiyonat yo'liga kiradi va butun umrini vijdon azobida o'tkazadi.

Romanning eng muhim obrazlaridan yana biri tarixchi Muhammadjon aka obrazidir. U ilmning qadr-qimmatini biladigan, ammo zamondan qadr topmagan odam sifatida

tasvirlanadi. Keksayib, tez-tez kasal bo'lib qoladigan Muhammadjon akaning bog'i va qushlari uning yagona suyanchi va ovunchog'iga aylanadi. Shu bilan birga, yozuvchi shu qushlar orqali ramziy ma'no yasashga urinadi. O'limiga yaqin qushlarini qafasdan ozod qilishi mamlakatning ozod bo'lishi va yosh nihollarning yetishib kelayotganidan xabar beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, romanda hayot yo'llari chalkashlik va arosatda qolib ketgan odamlar tasvirlangan. Ulardan biri ilm yo'lida, ma'rifat izlab, odamlarni ziyoli qilish uchun yurgan, mamlakat tarixini ortiqcha bo'yoqlarsiz yozib, avlodlarga qoldirishni niyat qilgan bo'lsa, ayrimlari mansab yo'lida o'zini fido qilib, oxirida hech narsasiz qoladi, yana biri eng boy tadbirkor bo'lishiga qaramay oiladan xalovat topmaydi, boshqalari qadr- qimmat ko'rmay, orzulari ushalmay dunyoni tark etsa, yana ba'zilar hayot yo'llarida arosatda qoladilar, nima qilarini bilmay, muvozanatni yo'qotadilar. Qahramonlarning hech biri na baxt, na xalovat, na- da sevgi topadilar...

Romanda tasvirlangan har bir obraz yangi davr ostonasida turgan insonlarning hayotdagi muvozanatsizlik holatini, ularning adoqsiz o'y-xayollari-yu iztiroblarini yoritib bergan.

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TO‘RA SULAYMON SHE‘RIYATIDA SHEVAGA XOS SO‘ZLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola To‘ra Sulaymon va uning ijodidagi ayrim she‘rlar va she‘riy parchalar, xususan, “Gul bir yon, chaman bir yon” she‘riy to‘plamidagi ba‘zi qismlarda shoirning dialektalogiyaga oid so‘zlarni qo‘llash mahorati haqida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: To‘ra Sulaymon, she‘r, sheva, shoir, ijod, dialekt, parcha, lahja.

She‘riyat - inson ruhining eng nozik tovushi, qalbning eng chuqur sukunatidan tug‘ilgan so‘zdir. Har bir she‘r - bu yurakning ichki olami bilan olam o‘rtasidagi ko‘prik, ko‘rinarli so‘zlar ortidagi ko‘rinmas hisdir. Shoir so‘z bilan emas, tuyg‘u bilan yozadi; u so‘zlarni yaratmaydi, balki ularni his qiladi. She‘riyat - bu insonning sukutdagi hayqirig‘i, ko‘z yoshidagi nur, tabassumdagi og‘riqdir. U hayotning tashqi shovqinidan emas, ruhning ichki jimligidan tug‘iladi. Shu boisdan ham she‘r - vaqtga sig‘maydigan, lekin har davrga tegishli san‘atdir. She‘riyatni anglash - bu insonning o‘zini anglashidir. Chunki har bir satr, har bir misra aslida shoirning emas, insoniyat ruhining so‘zlaridir. Bir gap bilan aytganda she‘riyat-ma‘naviyatni yuksaltiruvchi eng kuchli vositalardan biri. Birinchi prezidentimizning quyidagi so‘zlari ham aynan ma‘naviyatga oiddir: “Xalqning ma‘naviy ruhini mustahkamlash va rivojlantirish – O‘zbekistonda davlat va Jamiyatning eng muhim vazifasidir. Ma‘naviyat shunday qimmatbaho mevaki, u bizning qadimiy va navqiron xalqimiz qalbida butun Insoniyatning ulkan oilasida o‘z mustaqilligini tushunib yetish va ozodlikni sevish tuyg‘usi bilan birgalikda yetilgan. Ma‘naviyat insonga ona suti, ota namunasi, ajdodlar o‘giti bilan birga singadi” [1, 7].

“Odami ersang, demagil odami, Onikim yo‘q xalq g‘amidin g‘ami [2, 60]. Navoiyning ushbu jumlasiga xos va mos tarzda umr kechirgan va ijod qilgan adib To‘ra Sulaymondur. Xalq yuragidan chiqqan shoir, deya ta‘riflangan To‘ra Sulaymon mazmunli umri davomida o‘zining she‘riy qalami bilan o‘quvchilar ko‘nglidan joy olgan yetuk insondir. Uning sodda va barcha uchun birdek manzur bo‘lgan satrlari yillar davomida ma‘lum va mashhurdir. Shoir ijodida mehr, sadoqat, Vatanga muhabbat, onaga ehtirom kabi insoniyli tuyg‘ulari asosiy o‘rinni egallar ekan, “Istar ko‘ngil”, “Men qayga borar bo‘lsam”, “Iltijo”, “Qorako‘zginam”, “Sirdaryo qo‘shiqlari”, “Gul bir yon, chaman bir yon” kabi bir qancha to‘plamlarini o‘qib bunga amin bo‘lamiz. Quyida “Armon she‘ridagi parchaga e‘tibor beraylik:

Xeshlarimning bemavrid

Ko‘zlarida yosh ko‘rsam,

Ko‘nglimda armon yotar

terskaydagi qor misol...

Bu yerda “xesh” va “terskay” so‘zlari shevaga oid so‘zlardir. “Xesh” qipchoq lahjasiga oid so‘z bo‘lib, adabiy tildagi ma‘nosi “qarindosh-urug” deganidir. Xususan, qozoq tilida “xesh-zhurt”, qoraqalpoq tilida “xesh” so‘zlari huddi shu qarindosh ma‘nosida qo‘llaniladi.

“Terskay” so‘zi ham qipchoq lahjasiga oid bo‘lib, adabiy tilda “tog‘ning soyali qismi” ma‘nosida keladi.

Huddi shu she‘rning boshqa baytiga nazar tashlaymiz:

Aro yo‘lda qolguday bo‘lsa biror yo‘ldoshim,

Manzilga yetmay turib, qoqilsa qayg‘udoshim,

*Muhtoj bo‘lsa kimgadir, jon ayamas **qurdoshim,***

Badkor degan nom olsa biror bir vatandoshim...

Parchada ajratib ko'rsatilgan "qurdosh" so'zi qipchoq lahjasiga oid shevaga xos so'z bo'lib, "qardosh" (do'st, birodar) so'zining fonetik variantidir.

To'plamdagi "O'xshar" she'rining
Kelinchak bor uyning ko'rki bo'lakcha,
Boshida ukpary, **bo'rki** bo'lakcha...

"Bo'rk" so'zi ilk marta adabiyotda Mahmud Koshg'ariyning "Devonu lug'atit-turk" asarida uchraydi. Adabiy nutqdagi ma'nosi esa "qalpoq", "bosh kiyim"dir.

To'ra Sulaymonning ijodidan bir chimdim tahlil qilar ekanmiz beixtiyor Ozod Sharafiddinovning quyidagi jumllarini eslaymiz: "To'ra Sulaymon bizga juda kerak odam edi. Bizning hayotimiz uchun zarur bo'lgan odam edi, mafkuramiz uchun zarur bo'lgan odam edi"[6, 38].

"O'zbek she'riyatida ruhiy tasvir ko'rinishi va tamoyllari turli davrlarda turli shakllarda zohir bo'lgan. Chunki she'riyat davr nafasi, o'sha davr kishisi ruhiy olamida kechuvchi Jarayonlarning lirik qahramonlarning ruhiy dunyosi bilan uyg'un manzaralaridan yaraluvchi san'at mulkidir. Shuning uchun she'riyatdagi ruhiyat tasviri xususiyatlarini davr xarakteridan ajralgan holda tasavvur etish yoki tadqiq qilish haqiqatga muvofiq kelmaydi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan turib, ishda XX asr o'zbek she'riyatining har bir taraqqiyot bosqichiga xos bo'lgan ruhiyat tasvirining namoyon bo'lish darajalari uning lirik she'riyat rivojidadagi o'rni va ahamiyatini o'rganishga harakat qilindi [4]. Ushbu ma'lumotlarga uyg'un tarzda ijod qilgan To'ra Sulaymonning navbatdagi "Ayro" she'ridagi parchani havola qilamiz:

Nor qo'zg'alar bo'ldi o'rnidan
Moya qoldi moyalgicha...

Qipchoq lahjasiga oid "moya" so'zi adabiy tilda "urg'ochi hayvon" ma'nosida qo'llaniladi. To'ra Sulaymon esa o'z shevasida moya deya yozadi. Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshevning "Sensiz yolg'iz, g'arib qoldim" kitobida keltirgan "Chin ijodkorning ikki umri bo'ladi. Biri - barcha qatori "besh kunlik" deb atalguvchi hayot, ikkinchisi - o'zi o'tganidan so'ng asarlarida davom qiladigan yozuvchilik umri... To'ra Sulaymon el nazaridagi shoir edi. Uning bitganlari hayotligidayoq ko'p bosilgan, kuylangan ular haqda yozilgan. Uning chop qilinmay qolib ketgan asarlari juda ko'p emas. To'ra aka o'z bitiklariga aslo beparvo emasdi. U juda uzoq yillar oldin yozilgan va bosib chiqarilgan asarlarini ham qayta-qayta ko'zdan kechirib, lozim o'rinlarini tahrir qilardi..." [3, 5] jumllarga nazar tashlar ekanmiz, To'ra Sulaymonning yozuvchilik umrining mevalari naqadar shirin va barakali ekanligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Shoirning "Bolajon" she'rida
Ko'ngilga yovuqsan ko'z bilan qoshday,
G'ubori yo'q tongda chiqqan quyoshday...

"Yovuq" so'zi qipchoq lahjasiga oid so'z bo'lib adabiy tilda "juda chiroyli", "istarali", "ko'ngilga yaqin", "yoqimli" ma'nolarida kela oladi.

To'ra Sulaymon ijodining asosiy qismini uning she'rlari tashkil etadi. Qo'shiqchi shoir sifatida e'tirof etiladigan To'ra Sulaymon she'riyati ohangdorligi hamda ritmning xalqona ohanglarga yaginaligi bilan xarakterlanadi. Uning she'riyatga oid qalami 1960-1975 yillargacha tebranib turdi. Ernest Hemingueyda bunday hazilomuz gap bor: "Yozuvchi bo'lish uchun iste'dod bilan baxtsiz bolalik kifoya qiladi". Huddi shunday Baxmalning Aldashmon qishlog'ida tug'ilib o'sgan shoir yozuvchilik, shoirlik, bir ma'noda insoniylik tuyg'ulariga tom ma'noda mos umr kechirdi, deb bemalol aytish mumkin.

Xulosa

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish kerakki, To'ra Sulaymon ijodi o'zbek xalqining ruhiy olami, turmush tarzi va milliy qadriyatlarini she'riy ifoda etgan noyob manbalardan biridir. Uning she'riyatida qo'llanilgan shevaga xos so'zlar xalq tilining tabiiyligini, jonliligini va o'ziga

xos ohangdorligini saqlab qoladi. Bu soʻzlar orqali shoir xalq hayotini, urf-odatlarini va ichki kechinmalarini yanada yaqinroq ifodalagan. Shevaga xos birliklarning badiiy matnda ishlatilishi asarlarga samimiyat, tabiiylik va milliy ruh baxsh etadi. Shu bois Tora Sulaymon sheʼriyatini oʻrganish nafaqat tilshunoslik, balki xalqning madaniy boyligini anglash nuqtayi nazaridan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shoir ijodidagi shevaga xos soʻzlar oʻzbek adabiy tilining boyligiga boylik qoʻshib, milliy sheʼriyatimizni yanada rang-barang va ifodali qilgan.

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OʻTKIR HOSHIMOVNING “DUNYONING ISHLARI” ASARIDA YOZUVCHI NUTQIGA XOS BIRLIKLARNING IFODALANISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Oʻtkir Hoshimovning “Dunyoning ishlari” asarida yozuvchi nutqiga xos birliklarning ifodalanishi tahlil qilinadi. Asarda xalqona soʻzlar, maqollar, obrazli ifodalar, hissiy ohangdagi birliklar, shuningdek, milliy ruhni aks ettiruvchi soʻz boyliklarining qoʻllanilishi oʻrganilgan. Maqola yozuvchi uslubining hayotiyliigi, xalqona tabiati va oʻzbek xalqining ruhiyati bilan bogʻliqligini ochib beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Oʻtkir Hoshimov, “Dunyoning ishlari”, yozuvchi nutqi, xalqona birliklar, maqollar, obrazli ifoda.

Oʻzbek adabiyoti tarixida inson qalbini, uning dard-u izzatini, hayotga boʻlgan qarashlarini samimiy va haqqoniy tarzda tasvirlay olgan yozuvchilar koʻp. Ular orasida Oʻtkir Hoshimov nomi alohida oʻrin tutadi. Uning asarlari xalq hayotiga juda yaqin, xalq tilida yozilgan boʻlib, unda insoniy fazilatlar, vijdon, sabr-toqat va mehr-muhabbat asosiy mavzular sifatida gavdalanadi. Oʻtkir Hoshimov 1941-yil 5-avgust kuni Toshkent shahrida tugʻilgan. U Toshkent davlat universitetining jurnalistika fakultetini tugatgan. Mehnat faoliyatini matbuot sohasida boshlagan, keyinchalik yozuvchilik va jamoatchilik faoliyatini davom ettirgan. Yozuvchining “Dunyoning ishlari” nomli hikoyalar toʻplami oʻzbek adabiyotida xalqona hikoyachilikning yuksak namunasi hisoblanadi. Asarlarda oddiy insonlar hayoti, ularning orzu-umidlari, dard-u shodliklari samimiy tarzda tasvirlanadi. Muallif oʻz qahramonlari orqali oʻquvchini oʻylashga, hayotning mohiyatini anglashga undaydi.

Oʻtkir Hoshimov ijodining markazida inson va uning vijdoni turadi. U har bir inson oʻz vijdoni bilan yashasa, jamiyatda adolat, tinchlik va totuvlik boʻlishiga ishonadi. Shuning uchun ham uning asarlarida axloqiy poklik, halollik, insonparvarlik kabi gʻoyalar yetakchi oʻrin tutadi.

“Dunyoning ishlari” qissasi haqida Oʻzbekiston xalq yozuvchisi Said Ahmad shunday degandi: “Dunyoning ishlari” asarini qissa emas, doston deb atashni istardim. U qoʻshiqday oʻqiladi. Uni oʻqib turib, oʻz onalarimizni oʻylab ketamiz. Shu mushfiq, shu jafokash onalarimiz oldidagi bir umr uzib boʻlmas qarzlrimizning aqalli bittasini uza oldikmi, degan

bir andisha, bir savol ko‘z oldimizga ko‘ndalang turib oladi. Qissa bizni insofga, insonni qadrlashga, hurmat qilishga chaqiradi”[3].

“Taniqli adib O‘tkir Hoshimovning “Dunyoning ishlari” qissasi kitobxonlar qalbidan chuqur joy olgan asardir. Unda asar voqealari muallif nutqi bilan emas, balki personaj nutqi, ya‘ni hikoyachi qahramon tilidan hikoya qilinadi. “Dunyoning ishlari” bir qarashda avtobiografik qissaga o‘xshaydi. Unda muallif o‘z onasi to‘g‘risida, urush yillarida kechgan bolaligi to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritadi” [2, 143].

O‘tkir Hoshimovning “Dunyoning ishlari” asarida yozuvchi nutqida xalqona ohangni ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Masalan, asar ichidagi “Gilam paypoq” hikoyasidagi Hoji buvi va Poshsha obrazlari tilida:

-Voy Poshsha-a-a! Nima qilib qo‘ydingiz, tamom bo‘psiz-ku!

-Oyog‘ingizdan ayrilibsiz-ku!

kabi gaplar orqali Hoji buvining tilidan keltirilgan xalqona gaplarni ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

-Oyi, Dalavoy keldi! - dedi akam hovliqib.

Oyim sakrab o‘rnidan turib ketdi.

-Voy sho‘rim! Ertalabdan buyon o‘ng qovog‘im uchayotgan edi-ya. Bu ko‘rgulik ham bor ekan.

Ushbu jumlada obrazlarning xalqona so‘zlashuvi keltirilgan. Yana shuningdek, yozuvchi o‘z qahramonlarini aynan xalq tili, jonli so‘zlashuv uslubi orqali ifodalaydi. Masalan asarda “ona uchun bolaning katta-kichigi bo‘lmaydi”, “haqiqat havoga o‘xshaydi”, “nafas olib turasiz-u, o‘zini ko‘rmaysiz” kabi ko‘plab chuqur ma‘noli iboralar ham keltirilgan. Bu iboralar orqali yozuvchi hayot haqiqatini sodda, ammo chuqur ma‘noda ifodalaydi.

Yozuvchining nutqida xalq maqollari va iboralar ham tez-tez uchrab turadi. Ular nafaqat badiiy bezak, balki xalq donoligini ifoda etuvchi vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. Masalan:

“Oshsiz uy bor, urushsiz uy yo‘q” - yozuvchi ushbu maqol orqali har qanday uyda, oilada ham kichik-kichik muammolar bo‘lib turishi va ularga ota-ona o‘rtasidagi mehr-muhabbat va o‘zaro hurmat orqali yechim topish mumkinligini yozuvchi ko‘rsatib bera oladi.

Yana shuningdek, “Dunyoning ishlari” asarida perimiologik birliklar ham qo‘llanilgan. “Gilam paypoq” hikoyasida Hoji buvi qahramoni tilidan aytilgan “Vahima qilmang, dardini bergan Xudo shifosini ham beradi” deb aytadi. Bu so‘z ham diniy, ham ma‘naviy ma‘noda keltirgan. Ollah bergan sinovlarga sabr-toqat, umid qilib yengishini nazarda tutgan. Bu ibora bir tomondan Ollah sinovini eslatga, boshqa tomondan sabr va iymonning kuchi haqida eslatadi.

Asarda ko‘p hollarda yozuvchi dialogik shaklda foydalanadi. Qahramonlarning suhbatlarini sun‘iy emas, balki tabiiy, xalq og‘zaki nutqiga yaqin qilib tasvirlaydi.

-Qarz? Hali birovdan qarz ham olasizmi?

-E, senga nima, bolam! Mening ishimga aralashib nima qilasan?

Ushbu dialogik nutq “Qarz” hikoyasida keltirilgan. Ushbu hikoyada mehr-muhabbat, insoniylik kabi xislatlar ifodalangan. Dialoglar asarlarning hissiy ta‘sirini kuchaytiradi.

Asarda emotsional va ekspressiv birliklar ham qo‘llanilgan. Yozuvchi nutqida histuyg‘ularni ifodalovchi so‘zlar keng qo‘llaniladi: bechora, sho‘rlik, iltijo, yurak ezildi, yig‘lab yubordi, yuragi orqaga qaytdi kabi so‘zlar asarga hissiy boylik bag‘ishlaydi.

Bu so‘zlar o‘quvchini befarq qoldirmaydi, ularni qahramonlar bilan birga iztiroblar va quvonchni his qilishga undaydi. “Dunyoning ishlari” qissasidagi so‘nggi hikoya “Iltijo”da yozuvchi shu darajada mahorat bilan yozganki, o‘qigan har bir kitobxonni ta‘sirlantirib, ko‘ziga yosh keltiradi. Ona obrazi keltirilgan har qanday asar kitobxonni befarq qoldirmaydi. “Iltijo” hikoyasida keltirilgan muallif va uning onasining qabri boshidagi suhbat kitobxon

qalbining tub-tubigacha yetib boradi. “Oyi, men keldim... Eshityapsanmi, oyi, men yana keldim... Bugun... o‘zingizning ustingizdan boychechak o‘sib chiqibdi... Yo‘q, ha, oyijon... Yig‘layotganim yo‘q. Bilaman, men yig‘lasam, siz bezovta bo‘lasiz. Hozir... hozir o‘tib ketadi. Mana bo‘ldi...”[1, 174]. Ushbu ta‘sirli jumlar har bir kitobxonni tuyg‘ularini junbushga keltirmay qo‘ymaydi.

“Dunyoning ishlari” qissasida xalq og‘zaki ijodi namunalari ham keng ravishda qo‘llanilgan. “Oltin Baldoq” hikoyasida ham xalq og‘zaki ijodi namunasi bo‘lgan kelin salom keltirilgan.

Karmonni katta ochgan
Ayamay pulni sochgan,
Qorinlari qopday,
Mo‘ylovlari shopday
Qaynotasiga salo-o-m!

yoki qo‘shiq janri ham keltirilgan.

“Tolda chumchuq sayraydi, ko‘rsam, ko‘nglim yayraydi...” kabi qo‘shiq janri “Ermon buvaning tilagi” hikoyasida keltirilgan.

“Dunyoning ishlari” asarida O‘tkir Hoshimov o‘zbek xalq tilining boy imkoniyatlarini to‘liq namoyon etgan. Yozuvchi nutqidagi xalqona birliklar, maqollar, dialoglar va falsafiy ohanglar asarga hayotiylik, samimiyat va chuqurlik baxsh etgan.

Shu jihatdan O‘tkir Hoshimov nafaqat adib, balki xalq ruhining tarjimoni, tilning mahoratli egasi sifatida o‘zbek adabiyotida muhim o‘rin egallaydi.

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TOHIR MALIK IJODIDA TEOLOGIK TUSHUNCHALAR IFODASI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek adabiyotining zabardast vakili Tohir Malik ijodidagi teologik tushunchalarning badiiy va hayot falsafasi sifatida talqini, ularning inson ruhiyati, imon va vijdon bilan bog‘liq mazmuni, ruhiy poklanish va adolat g‘oyalari tahlil qilinadi. Yozuvchi asarlarida e‘tiqod, sabr, tavba, taqdir kabi diniy va falsafiy tushunchalarning xalqona va zamonaviy talqini o‘zaro uyg‘unlikda yoritilgan bo‘lib, xalq tiliga yaqin, kitobxonning qalbidan joy oladigan sodda va ravon tilda yozilganligi haqida so‘z yuritilgan. Tohir Malik maqola adibning asarlaridagi til, uslub va ma‘naviy qatlamlarni ochib berishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tohir Malik, teologik tushunchalar, imon, tavba, taqdir, vijdon, badiiy tahlil, ma‘naviyat.

Adabiyot har doim inson ruhiyatining oynasi bo‘lib kelgan. Shu bois o‘zbek adabiyotida teologik qarashlar, ya‘ni diniy va axloqiy g‘oyalar yozuvchi dunyoqarashining ajralmas qismidir. O‘zbek adabiyotida insonning ma‘naviy olamini, e‘tiqodini va imon sinovlarini chuqur tasvirlagan ijodkorlardan biri - Tohir Malikdir. Uning asarlari nafaqat adabiy hodisa, balki ma‘naviy ogohlik maktabidir. Adib o‘z qahramonlari orqali hayotning

murakkab, ba'zan ziddiyatli manzaralarini chizadi. Shu jarayonda u "taqdir", "tavba", "gunoh", "sabr", "vijdon" kabi teologik tushunchalarni tilning badiiy imkoniyatlari orqali chuqur ifoda etadi. Tohir Malik ijodi orqali o'quvchi insonning ichki olami, ruhiy iztiroblari, e'tiqodi bilan yuzlashadi. Bu asarlar diniy nasihat emas, balki hayotiy haqiqat va ruhiy o'zgarishning badiiy ifodasidir. Tohir Malik uchun e'tiqod va vijdon muvozanati – bu insonning ichki tuyg'usi, ruhiy harakati, o'zini anglash yo'lidir. Yozuvchi uchun teologiya - bu insonning ichki dunyosini tahlil etuvchi ruhiy ko'zgudir. Teologik tushunchalarning badiiy ko'rinishi Tohir Malik asarlarida badiiy nutqning asosiy qatlamini tashkil etadi. Quyidagi jihatlar bunga yaqqol misol bo'ladi:

“Taqdir” – yozuvchi uchun oldindan belgilangan yo'l emas, balki insonning o'zi tanlagan yo'li.

“Tavba” – bu kechirim so'rash emas, balki o'z xatosini tan olib, ruhiy o'zgarish sari tashlangan qadam.

“Sabr” – har bir insonning sinovi, taqdir oldidagi bardoshi.

“Gunoh” – bu yovuzlik emas, balki insonning zaifligi, uni tuzatish uchun berilgan imkon. Bu tushunchalar yozuvchi asarlarida psixologik holat bilan o'zaro uyg'unlashgan. Har bir qahramon o'z "ichki tavbasi" ni boshidan kechiradi. Yozuvchi diniy so'zlarni ma'naviy-axloqiy g'oya bilan birlashtirib, ularni o'zbek tilining ifoda boyligida yangicha talqin etadi. Til va uslubda teologik qatlam Tohir Malikning tili o'zbek xalqining tafakkuriga yaqin, ammo unda ilohiy ma'nolar tizimi yashiringan. U Qur'on oyatlaridan bevosita iqtibos bermaydi, biroq ularning mazmunini xalqona so'z bilan ifodalaydi. O'quvchi uchun Tohir Malik asarlari ma'naviy saboq, diniy targ'ibot emas, balki ruhiy tahlil maydonidir. Insonni o'ylashga, o'zini ko'rishga, imyon bilan yashashga undaydigan asarlari **“Shaytanat”** to'rt qismdan iborat bo'lgan va keyinchalik filmga moslashtirilgan mashhur romani. **“Falak”** ilmiy-fantastik janrdagi qissa. **“So'nggi o'q”** qissa va hikoyalardan iborat to'plam unda gunoh, jazo va kechirim masalalari insoniy dramalar bilan bog'langan. **“Hikmat afandining o'limi”** yozuvchining ilk yirik asari. **“Alvido, bolalik”** boshqa mashhur asarlaridan biri. **“Bir kecha, bir ko'cha”** yana bir taniqli hikoyasi. **“Imonlashish umidi”** asari bu asar **“Mehmon tuyg'ular”** kitobining tuzatilgan ikkinchi nashri xisoblanib, odamzotning oxiratdagi o'rni niyati va ammallariga bogliqligiga qaratilganligi to'g'risida yozuvchi til vositasida e'tiqodning badiiy tilini yaratgan. Shu orqali Tohir Malik asarlarida teologik semantika bilan milliy ruh birlashgan. Bu jihat uni nafaqat adabiy, balki ma'naviy hodisaga aylantiradi.

“Shaytanat” asarida yozuvchi insonning gunoh va tavba o'rtasidagi kurashini nafaqat voqealar orqali, balki til orqali ham ko'rsatadi. Bunda "shaytanat" dunyosi juda keng bo'lib, borgan sari bu olamga bilib-bilmay, adashib kirib keluvchilar evaziga kengayaveradi. Maqsad esa bitta – boyluk, lekin to'plangan boylukdan aqalli bir tangani o'zi bilan u dunyoga olib keta olmasligini anglashmagan. Aynan shu qo'lning kiri uchun vijdonidan kechib shaytonning yo'rig'iga kirgan kimsalar o'zlariga hasad, xiyonat, zulm kabi illatlarni hamroh qilishgan. Roman qahramoni Asadbek obrazida yozuvchi "vijdon azobi" ni teologik jihatdan ochib beradi. Har bir so'z, ibora - "Alloh saqlasin", "Taqdirning ishi", "Tavba qilish kerak" - bu faqat tildagi birlik emas, ruhiy jarayonning ko'zgidir. Tohir Malik tili xalqona, ammo ma'naviy jihatdan yuksak. U diniy tushunchalarni o'quvchining hayotiy tajribasiga yaqinlashtiradi. Shu bois "Shaytanat" faqat jinoyat haqida emas - gunohning ichki og'rig'i, insonning imyon sinovi haqidagi asardir.

Yozuvchi asarlarida **“shayton”** obrazining o'zi ham ramziy ma'noga ega. Bu – insonning ichidagi **nafs**, yovuzlik, vasvasa timsoli. Bilamizki nafs insonni yomon narsalarga buyuradi. Inson zoti unga quloq soldimi, tamom, nafsining quliga aylanadi. Inson aslida Haqning quli, nafsning quli emas. Asarda "Jalilning "Xudodan qaytibdi" degan gapi ham shunaqa"[2,580] har qanday ishlarimiz hamda ammalarimiz uchun Ollohning ajri borligini doimo unutmashimiz lozim. Zero,

yozuvchi **“Odamiylik mulki”** asarida “Kimki o‘zining yaxshi amalidan xursanl bo‘lib, yomon amalidan xafa bolsa, u mo‘mindir.”[4,87] Bunday dunyo haqiqatlarini **“Imonlashish umidi”** asarida ham keng yoritib bergan. “Ozod odam hech bir to‘siqsiz egalik qilishi mumkun bo‘lgan narsaga egadir. Xech bir to‘siqsiz nimaga egalik qilish mumkin? Faqat O‘Z-O‘ZIGA! Agar siz odamning o‘z-o‘ziga egalik qilmay, boshqalarga ham xukum o‘tkazmoqqa jazm etganini ko‘rsangiz, bilingkim, u ozod emasdir. U boshqalarga xokimlik qilishni istadimi, demak, u o‘z istagi - nafsi qulidir.”[5,3] Shu orqali adib ma‘naviy kurashni badiiy shaklda ifoda etadi. Bugungi adabiyotda bunday tahlil zarur. Chunki teologik tushunchalar – bu diniy masala emas, balki eng avvalo insoniy ong va axloqning ildizidir.

Tohir Malik teologik tushunchalarni jamiyat axloqining mustahkamlanishiga xizmat qiluvchi vosita sifatida talqin etadi. Uning asarlaridagi ruhiy iztirob, tavba, sabr va e‘tiqod kabi g‘oyalar o‘quvchini o‘z vijdoni bilan suhbatga chorlaydi. Yozuvchi nafaqat diniy mavzuni, balki insoniy mas‘uliyatni ham markazga qo‘yadi. Yozuvchi diniy tushunchalarni insoniy tajriba, ruhiy iztirob va ma‘naviy tozalik bilan bog‘lab, o‘z ijodini falsafiy darajaga ko‘targan. Shu sababli, Tohir Malik asarlari bugungi kunda ham o‘quvchini iymon, sabr, vijdon va adolat kabi abadiy qadriyatlarga chorlaydi.

Xulosa o‘rnida aytishimiz mumkinki, Tohir Malik o‘zbek adabiyotiga teologik tafakkurni badiiy nutqqa singdirgan adib sifatida kirgan bo‘lib, teologik tafakkurning yangi bosqichini boshlab bergan. Uning asarlarida din va hayot, ruhiyat va adolat bir butun holda ko‘riladi. Adib asarlarida teologik motivlar nafaqat diniy ma‘rifat, balki milliy o‘zlik va axloqiy ongni shakllantirish vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Shu bois, Tohir Malik ijodini o‘rganish adabiy, falsafiy va ma‘naviy jihatdan ham muhimdir.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РАБОТЫ АБДУЛЛЫ АВЛОНИ «ТУРКИЙ ГУЛИСТАН ЁХУД АХЛОК»

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Аннотация: Важное влияние на формирование духовной среды в обществе оказывает сфера воспитания молодежи нации, и ее важность подчеркивается также следующими предложениями в творчестве Абдуллы Авлони, одного из зрелых представителей просветители: «Туркий гулистан ёхоуд ахлок»: «Образование – это вопрос жизни – или смерти, или спасения – или разрушения, или счастья – или катастрофы». По этой причине процесс воспитания молодежи в нашей стране, особенно духовного воспитания, так актуален, важен и даже поднят на уровень государственной политики. Это факт, что система образования, не отвечающая требованиям времени, должна быть полностью реформирована с первых дней независимости нашей страны.

Из работы Абдуллы Авлони в виде брошюры мы видим, что моральные нормы, необходимые для формирования нравственных качеств при воспитании молодого поколения, имеют систематизированную форму. Если в XX веке период национального возрождения имел большое значение в развитии идей, то в XXI веке он будет иметь особое значение в создании Ушиншинского Возрождения в Новом Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: «Туркий гулистан ёхоуд ахлок», образование – воспитание, просвещение, «Гулистан», нравственность, гармония тела и души, воспитание мысли, Родина, воспитание совершенного поколения.

На нашей Родине Республика Узбекистан отметила славное 32-летие своего независимого развития под лозунгом «Это новая жизнь, это Новый Узбекистан» как самый большой и дорогой праздник. Этот период был поистине великим периодом в истории нашей страны, написанным золотыми буквами.

Вот уже тридцать два года наш народ идет по пути великого развития, не сворачивая.

В частности, за прошедший период была проведена образцовая работа в сфере воспитания молодежи, воспитания ее знающих, умелых и профессиональных, поднятия морального духа молодежи, повышения ее политического сознания и правовой культуры. В 1992 году принят первый в нашем независимом Узбекистане Закон «Об образовании», в 1997 году – Национальная программа подготовки кадров, в 2016 году – Закон «Об основах государственной политики в сфере молодежи в Республике Узбекистан», В 2018 году – решение «О мерах по воспитанию молодежи в духовно, нравственном и физическом совершенстве, поднятию качества их системы образования на новый уровень», в 2020 году «Молодёжи в Республике Узбекистан указ о радикальной реформе» государственной политики в сфере молодежи и мерах по ее выводу на новый уровень», в 2021 году приняты и реализованы на практике решения

«Об утверждении концессии на развитие государственной политики в сфере молодежи в Узбекистане до 2025 года». быть примером нашего мнения выше.

В частности, Президент Республики Узбекистан Шавкат Мирзиёев уделяет особое внимание вопросам воспитания молодых людей, психически зрелых, физически здоровых, духовно зрелых, являющихся продолжением нашей жизни.

«Известно, что наши предки считали знания, образование и обучение бесценным богатством, важнейшим условием и залогом человеческой зрелости и развития нации. Конечно, образование – продукт сознания, но в то же время уровень сознания и его развитие – важнейший фактор, формирующий и обогащающий духовность. Образование нельзя отделить от образования, а образование нельзя отделить от образования – это восточный взгляд, восточная философия жизни», – сказал наш первый президент Ислам Каримов [1].

Именно поэтому наши великие предки уделяли вопросам образования особое внимание, какой бы отраслью науки они ни занимались. Например, «Город добродетельных людей» Фараби, «Птичий трактат» Ибн Сины, «Реликвии Древние народы», «Кутадгу Билиг» Юсуфа Хоса Хаджиба, «Кобуснома» Кайковуса, «Хибат уль хакаик» Ахмеда Юнгнаки, «Гулистан» Садия, «Махбуб уль кулуб» Алишера Навои, «Хайрат уль Аброр». нравственное воспитание человеческой личности.

К этой группе относится и произведение Абдуллы Авлани «Туркий гулистан йохуд ахлок».

Размышляя об образовании в нашей стране, мы вспоминаем значимые слова Абдуллы Авлани: «Образование – это вопрос жизни, смерти, спасения, разрушения, счастья или катастрофы».

Хотя эти ободряющие слова нашего прадеда, обещавшего изменить общество посредством просвещения, были сказаны 100 лет назад, наука и новые технологии значительно продвинулись вперед, расширились мировоззрение, понимание и воображение людей, образование. Даже сегодня, когда система образования вышел на новый уровень, он не потерял своего значения. Итак, каким бы технологически развитым ни было общество, каждый исторический период ставит новые и сложные вопросы, касающиеся духовно-образовательного развития человека и воспитания молодежи. Человечество осознает, что эта проблема всегда была в центре внимания ученых, философов и политологов, педагогов и тренеров.

Абдулла Авлани высказывает следующие мысли по поводу написания своего произведения «Туркий гулистан йохуд ахлок». В работе он говорил, что взял модель из «Гюлистана» Саади: «В школах Туркестана нет идеальной книги «Ахлок», написанной на нашем диалекте, дело в том, что африканская нация жаждет и нуждается в такой работы, включая самого учителя, любовник, как известно, умер. Поэтому, после опыта этих слепых времен, я счел достойным написать на манер уважаемого писателя Шейха Сади, даже если это трудная задача, для меня это святая задача и пережить этот недостаток.

С чего автору следует начать с хорошего образования? задает вопрос и улучшает нравственность! дает следующий ответ морали:

Мораль – это наука, побуждающая людей делать добро и отталкивающая их от зла. Книга, которая объясняет добродетель хорошего поведения и вред плохого поведения с помощью доказательств и примеров, называется этикой [2]. «Мораль» - это на самом деле слепота слова «поведение». Поведение у всех разное. Но есть одно общее: в любом поведении есть достоинства и пороки. Другими словами, в каждом человеке в той или иной степени есть и добро, и порок. Вот почему мораль

совершенствуется и украшается посредством образования. Целью воспитания должно быть максимальное избавление от пороков и пороков и дальнейшее совершенствование добродетелей и добродетелей.

Великий просветитель выдвигает идею гармонии тела и души в воспитании. Он сравнивает эти два явления с аурой (верхом) и подкладкой (работой) одной и той же одежды. «Тело и душа подобны правой и неправильной сторонам одного меча. Если тело не украшено чистотой, если оно не сохранено от вредных привычек, это все равно, что мыть подкладку после того, как на нее наложили соль, и грязь на ней всегда попадет на работу. Образование мышления необходимо для крепкого и здорового тела. Поэтому родителям не следует проявлять беспечность, когда их дети болеют, и их следует как можно скорее отвести к врачу» [2].

Великий просветитель, размышляя о том, кто должен осуществлять образование, сказал: «Кто занимается образованием? Где это делается? возникает вопрос. В этом вопросе первым является домашнее образование. Это материнский долг. Во-вторых, школьное и медресе образование. Это обязанность отца, учителя, наставника и правительства», и один человек сказал: «О каких матерях вы говорите, о матерях, которые необразованны, имеют плохую голову и глупы? Они дадут образование, которого у них нет». Здесь это слово разбивает человеку сердце и обжигает его сердце. Если мы скажем, что насчет его отца, то какого отца? Вы говорите об отцах, которые не знают цены знаниям, которые не знают цены знаний, которые не знают времени? Прежде всего, необходимо их воспитывать и воспитывать, - говорит он. Вот пример этого слова, которое тонет в реке удивления.

А как насчет учителей, какой учитель? Вы говорите о студентах, чьи цели высоки, чьи цели высоки, чьи уроки не являются строгими и которые никогда не были близки к реформе? Они должны знать свои обязанности, избавиться от своего эго, реформировать свои уроки в соответствии со временем и преподавать одновременно с экзаменом, говорит он.

После этого на сцену выходит образование мысли. Автор считает, что «разум совершенен и единственный бог людей». Ум совершенствуется на основе знаний и опыта. Чем больше он видит, тем ценнее он становится.

Воспитание мысли есть самая необходимая, священная задача, данная нам издревле и вверенная вниманию учителей и их совести. Мысль делает человека добрым и восторженным. Это образование нуждается в помощи учителей на следующей ступени, от образования учителя зависит сила, красота и широта мысли.

Родина. Город-страна, где родился каждый человек, называется его родиной. Каждый любит место, где он родился и вырос, больше своей жизни. Даже у животных есть чувство Родины. Если животное потеряет родину, оно не будет жить так комфортно, как на своей земле, жизнь его будет несчастна, а любовь к Родине всегда будет в уголке его языка.

Как мы, туркестанцы, любим свою родину больше, чем свою жизнь, арабы любят Аравию, самые холодные снежные и ледяные земли больше, чем другие земли. Если бы им это не нравилось, они бы покинули родину и эмигрировали в места с хорошим воздухом и легкой жизнью.

Наши деды говорили: «Не будь султаном в чужой стране, будь пастухом в своей стране».

Я не виноват, моя страна, мои горы,
Я ушел слишком рано, мои дорогие.
Развод заставляет меня скитаться

Мои дни и ночи полны печали.

Эти мысли нашего великого просветителя Абдуллы Авлони не потеряли своего значения и сегодня. Формирование патриотизма у молодежи связано с пониманием ею общности национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей. В формировании патриотизма особо важными ценностями считаются обычаи, обряды, традиции, связанные с национальным развитием, историей, культурой, искусством и литературой, образом жизни, нравственностью, верой и социальным духом народа. . Также среди ценностей, оказывающих сильное влияние на формирование патриотизма у молодежи, - родной язык и литература, национальные и религиозные праздники, различные национальные обряды, семейная жизнь, детство, родители, соседи, родственники - род, соседство, любовь, уважение к пожилым людям, доброта, сострадание, честность, верность, вера, вдохновение прекрасной природой нашей страны, наличие культуры ее сохранения.

Сегодня, в условиях бурного развития науки и техники, по мере того, как каждая страна строит свои планы на будущее, требованием времени является уделить особое внимание развитию способностей к реализации этих планов, повышению интеллектуального потенциала, к духовному обогащению. По этой причине в нашей стране проводится масштабная работа по воспитанию зрелого поколения и защите его прав. В частности, тот факт, что 60 процентов государственного бюджета на 2022 год направлено на социальную сферу, является ярким выражением заботы о наших будущих наследниках. Ведь необходимо, чтобы молодежь формировалась как поколение, которое воплотит в жизнь наши нынешние намерения, обеспечит развитие нашей страны, в полной мере проявит свой талант во всех сферах.

Президент нашей страны сказал: «Молодые люди с высокой квалификацией, современными знаниями, образованные в соответствии с современными требованиями, являются залогом решения наших экономических проблем».

В обществе всегда существовала потребность в способных, деловой, зрелых кадрах. История развития общества свидетельствует о потребности в квалифицированных кадрах для удовлетворения его потребностей и решения существующих проблем. На основе кадровой политики этого общества требуется непрерывная работа в области духовности и просвещения, регулярное развитие личности. Под совершенным человеком мы понимаем прежде всего просветленных людей, способных мыслить самостоятельно и стать примером для других.

Концепция воспитания идеального поколения имеет философский, политический смысл и содержание, а также основные элементы социальной политики, прежде всего коренные реформы в процессах взаимоотношений между политическими и социальными институтами.

Совершенное поколение и новое поколение кадров имеют гармоничное взаимопонимание, при котором:

- 1) новый человек самостоятелен, обладатель нового мышления и сознания;
- 2) освобождены от влияния единой господствующей идеологии;
- 3) воспитаны в духе национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей, получили знания, основанные на новых национальных образовательных стандартах, основанных на достижениях современной науки, строго готовили или совершенствовались свою квалификацию;
- 4) зрелое новое поколение – это новый слой, ценящий демократические принципы, обладающий высоким потенциалом, вооруженный современными

достижениями науки и техники, полностью осознающий ответственность за внесение практического вклада в повышение социально-экономического потенциала страны. .

Подготовка идеального поколения кадров ярко проявляется в демократическом характере государственной политики. Оно неразрывно связано с целями реализуемых демократических социальных и политических реформ, а Узбекистан, вставший на путь построения демократического общества, представляет собой новую политическую реальность.

В воспитании идеального поколения всегда используются в гармонии друг с другом два понятия:

1. Понятие образование – это дидактическая деятельность, осуществляемая совместно преподавателем и обучающимися в целях обеспечения развития личности путем достижения образовательного и образовательного уровня. Это система дидактических мероприятий, направленных на обеспечение психического развития человека.

2. Понятие образование - это социальная функция, обеспечивающая развитие людей нового поколения путем передачи им социально-исторического опыта старшего поколения, имеющая конкретную цель формирования, принятия решений, обогащения и совершенствования субъективно-исторического опыта. Личностный и духовный мир человека находится под влиянием социальных институтов, направленного, систематического и сознательного процесса.

Короче говоря, образование – это главное звено социализации, которое тесно связано с воспитанием, это составная часть системы образования. Наши предки издревле считали знания, образование и обучение важнейшим условием и залогом человеческого совершенствования и развития нации. Исходя из этой идеи, с первых лет независимости вопрос образования и обучения рассматривается как приоритетное направление нашей государственной политики, а уровень эффективности, достижения и недостатки системы образования и обучения, науки и образования рассматриваются как приоритетное направление нашей государственной политики. Проанализировано профессиональное обучение по всей стране. В целях совершенствования системы образования, полностью отвечающей требованиям современного развития, был принят ряд законов, постановлений и указов. Их суть направлена на воспитание зрелого поколения, и в нем определены следующие задачи. В частности, воспитывать молодое поколение зрелым на основе духовно-нравственного воспитания, широко и эффективно использовать средства массовой информации в воспитании и формировании духовности учащихся на основе национальной идеи, любить Родину и люди в молодежи, бороться за благополучие страны, гуманизм, Образовательные вопросы, такие как осознание природы, национальная гордость, национальная гордость, уважение к людям других национальностей и их ценностей, свобода совести, знаний, нравственность, физическая зрелость, самостоятельность мышления у молодежи выполняются как приоритетная задача. повышается.

Поэтому богатое наследие, оставленное Абдуллою Авлони, напрямую считается духовным достоянием нашего народа. Нам приятно узнать больше о том, что наши просвещенные предки, которые были национальными лидерами такого высокого уровня в тот сложный колониальный период, самоотверженно творили, своей практической деятельностью вносили свой вклад в повышение просвещения нации, и наслаждаются полнотой своих произведений. только честь независимости позволила нам быть такими. Зная эту историю, наслаждаясь жизнью и творчеством таких самоотверженных людей, примерами их творчества, наше духовное развитие сегодня

происходило не само собой, этому способствовали наши великие предки, люди-патриоты, подобные Авлони, даже всей своей жизнью. Он призывает нынешнее и будущие поколения знать, ценить и учиться у него тому, что он сделал в своем даре.

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SA'DULLA HAKIMNING "OLIS YULDUZ" DOSTONI HAQIDA MULOHAZALAR

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Annotatsiya: "Olis Yulduz" dostoni, insonning ichki dunyosidagi intilishlar va umidlar haqida hikoya qiladi. Doston insonning o'z maqsadlari sari intilishi, shu bilan birga, hayotning qiyinchiliklari va sinovlari bilan kurashish jarayonini tasvirlaydi. Falsafiy jihatdan bu asar, insonning o'z orzulariga erishish yo'lidagi sabr-toqati va matonatini ulug'laydi. Tarbiyaviy ahamiyati esa, o'quvchilarga maqsad sari intilish, orzularni ta'qib etish va hayot sinovlariga bardoshli bo'lish kabi qadriyatlarni singdiradi. Shuningdek, asar insonlarga o'z qobiliyatlariga ishonch hosil qilish va ularni rivojlantirishga undaydi. Ushbu maqolamiz shu haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Doston, obraz, bosh qahramon, poetika, ramziy-falsafiy asar, tip, dunyoqarash, to'qima obraz, tarixiy shaxs.*

Adabiyot insoniyat tafakkurining eng yuksak mahsuli bo'lib, uning eng nozik his-tuyg'ularini, orzu-umidlarini, ezgulik sari intilishlarini aks ettiradi. Shu boisdan, adabiy asarlar inson ruhiyatiga bevosita ta'sir etuvchi, uning dunyoqarashini shakllantiruvchi kuchli vosita sifatida qadrlanadi. Bu jihatdan "Olis yulduz" dostoni o'zining chuqur falsafiy mazmuni, tarixiy asoslari, ramziy obrazlari va badiiy go'zalligi bilan adabiyotimizning eng yuksak namunalari qatoridan munosib o'rin egallaydi. Ushbu doston nafaqat badiiy asar sifatida, balki inson ma'naviyati va ruhiy olamini yorituvchi falsafiy mushohada sifatida ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Dostonning o'qi – inson, uning orzu-intilishlari, ichki kurashlari va ma'naviy izlanishlaridir. "Olis yulduz" dostonida bu jihatlar chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Bosh qahramon Siprangiz obrazi orqali muallif insonning ruhi, orzusi va tafakkurining eng chuqur qatlamlariga kirib boradi. Sparangiz – shunchaki obraz emas, u o'zida butun bir ma'naviy maktabni mujassam etgan timsoldir. Uning harakati, qarorlari va kurashi orqali biz inson

qalbidagi ezgulik, mardlik va fidoyilik singari yuksak fazilatlarining yorqin aksini ko'ramiz.[1,74 b]

Tabiat faqat tashqi dunyo sifatida emas, balki insonning ruhiy kechinmalarini aks ettiruvchi bir o'lkaga aylangan. Doston davomida, Sparangiz va boshqa qahramonlar tabiatda o'zlarini yakkalanib, qo'rqib, hayajonlanib yoki baxtli his qilishadi. Misol uchun, dostonning ayrim joylarida o'tgan daryolar, tepalar va boshqa tabiiy manzaralar insonning ichki ruhiy holatiga va uning jamiyatdagi o'rniga ta'sir qiladigan omil sifatida ishlatiladi. Ushbu tabiatning kuchli tasviri orqali, insonning his-tuyg'ulari, baxt va umid izlanishlari, shuningdek, kurashlar va shafqatsizliklar aniq ko'rsatiladi.[2,304 b]

Tabiat bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lgan boshqa muhim jihat esa insonning tabiatni anglash va undan to'g'ri foydalanish masalasidir. "Olis yulduz" dostonida tabiat va inson o'rtasidagi bu bog'liqlikda har bir qahramon o'zining tabiiy muhitida, tabiatning qonunlariga rioya qilgan holda hayot kechiradi. Tabiat insonni tarbiyalaydi, unga kuch va iroda beradi, lekin inson ham tabiatni hurmat qilib, uning qonunlariga amal qilishi lozim.[3,119 b] Dostonning markazida joylashgan Mitra timsoli bu g'oyani ta'kidlaydi: Mitra, tabiatni, yer va osmonni boshqaruvchi kuch sifatida, insonlarga to'g'ri yo'l ko'rsatadi va ularni zulmatdan nurlikka olib chiqadi. Bu tabiiy qonunlarga bo'ysunish, shuningdek, insonning o'zaro munosabatlarini ham ijobiy yo'lda rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Tabiatning inson uchun muhim rol o'ynashi dostonning bir nechta voqealarida yoritilgan. Masalan, Sparangizning tabiiy muhitga bo'lgan munosabati, uning yurtini va xalqini sevishi, o'z hayotini va maqsadlarini tabiat bilan bog'lab tushunishi uning ruhiy kuchini oshiradi. Tabiatga qarshi chiqish yoki uni e'tiborsiz qoldirish, insonning yomonlikka va yovuzlikka qarshi kurashdagi zaifligini ko'rsatadi.[4,303b] Shunday qilib, tabiat bilan insonning munosabati faqat tashqi voqelik sifatida qolmay, balki ichki dunyoning shakllanishida va insonning ma'naviy o'sishida muhim omil bo'ladi.

Dostonning yakunida, Sparangiz va boshqa qahramonlarning tabiat bilan aloqasi orqali insoniyatning abadiy umidi va maqsadiga erishishi tasvirlanadi. Tabiat faqat tashqi dunyo emas, balki insonning ichki borligining bir qismi sifatida, uning baxtli yoki baxtsiz hayotini belgilovchi kuchdir. Bu bog'liqlik, inson va tabiatning o'zaro muvozanatda bo'lishi kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. Asar orqali o'quvchi tabiat va inson o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqani anglab, hayotning ma'nosini chuqurroq tushunadi.

"Olis yulduz" dostoni, insoniy hayotning eng asosiy tamoyillaridan biri – yaxshilik va yomonlikning abadiy kurashi haqida hikoya qiladi. Ushbu doston o'zining chuqur ma'nomazmuni va o'tkir badiiy tasvirlari orqali o'quvchini insoniy mohiyatning eng muhim savollarini o'ylashga undaydi. Doston voqealarida yaxshilik va yomonlikning o'zaro to'qnashuvi nafaqat tarixiy voqealar, balki inson qalbi va jamiyatdagi muammolar timsolida [5,3 b]ham namoyon bo'ladi.

Doston bosh qahramoni Sparangizning hayoti va taqdiri yaxshilik va yomonlikning ziddiyatli kurashi asosida rivojlanadi. U o'z xalqiga bo'lgan sadoqati, erkinlik uchun kurashi va insoniy fazilatlarini bilan namoyon bo'lsa, yomonlik esa nafaqat dushmanlar timsolida, balki ba'zan ichki ruhiy kurash shaklida ham o'zini ko'rsatadi. Bu holat insonning o'zini anglash jarayonidagi ziddiyatlarni ochib beradi.

Dostonda yaxshilikning ramzi sifatida Mitra – tinchlik va hayotbaxshlik timsoli ko'rsatilgan. Mitra insonlarni mashaqqatlardan olib chiqishga, yaxshilik va muhabbatni yoyishga da'vat etadi. Ushbu falsafiy g'oya Sparangizning harakatlarida ham aks etadi. Sparangiz jang maydonida ham, o'z shaxsiy hayotida ham adolat, halollik va insoniylik tamoyillariga amal qiladi. U yurtiga va o'z xalqiga bo'lgan sadoqati tufayli shaxsiy manfaatlarini qurbon qilishga tayyor.

Sparangizning harakatlari, ayniqsa, yurtini himoya qilish yo'lida qilgan fidokorliklari dostonning yaxshilikni ulug'lovchi markaziy fikrlaridan biridir. Uning qalbidagi vatanparvarlik, mehr-muhabbat va adolat hissi yaxshilikning inson qalbidagi qudratini ko'rsatadi. Bunday fazilatlar orqali Sparangiz o'zining kuchli ichki qahramonligini namoyish etadi.

Ushbu obraz adolat va halollik uchun kurashuvchi, xalqining ozodligi va baxt-saodati uchun o'zini qurbon qilishga tayyor bo'lgan inson timsolidir. Sparangizning xatti-harakatlari va qarorlari uning insoniy fazilatlarini ochib beradi, ayni paytda bu fazilatlar o'quvchiga ibrat bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Sparangizning har bir harakati uning insoniy fazilatlarini yuksak darajada ko'rsatadi. U yurtining mustaqilligi va tinchligini himoya qilish yo'lida fidokorlik qiladi. Dostondagi ko'plab voqealar shuni tasdiqlaydiki, Sparangiz uchun vatanparvarlik va sadoqat shaxsiy manfaatlardan ustun turadi. Uning harakatlari shuni ko'rsatadiki, haqiqiy qahramonlik nafaqat jang maydonida, balki ichki kurashlarda ham namoyon bo'ladi.[6,12 b]

Sparangiz obrazi nafaqat tashqi dushmanlarga qarshi kurashda, balki ichki ruhiy kurashlarda ham namoyon bo'ladi. Uning o'z-o'zi bilan olib borgan ichki kurashlari – bu insonning shaxsiy izlanishlari va ma'naviy o'sishining yorqin misoli. Dostondagi ba'zi voqealar uning shubhalari va qo'rquvlari haqida so'zlasa-da, oxir-oqibat u maqsadidan chekinmaslikni tanlaydi.

Sparangiz obrazi o'quvchi uchun haqiqiy ibrat namunasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Uning qahramonligi, fidoyiligi va adolatparvarligi hayotdagi ko'plab muammolarni qanday hal qilish mumkinligi haqida o'ylashga undaydi. Unga taqlid qilish orqali insonlar o'z ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishi va jamiyatga foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Sparangiz obrazi "Olis yulduz" dostoni markazida turuvchi va uning ma'nosini ochib beruvchi asosiy qahramonlardan biridir. Uning vatanparvarligi, jasorati va insoniyligi o'quvchi qalbida chuqur iz qoldiradi. Ushbu obraz adolat, sadoqat va tinchlik uchun kurashning abadiy qadriyat ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Sa'dulla Hakimning dostonlarining kompozitsiyasi, an'anaviy O'zbek adabiyotidan ilhomlanib, zamonaviy mavzular bilan uyg'unlashgan holda yaratiladi. Shoirning har bir asari o'ziga xos tuzilishga ega bo'lib, u muayyan bir qahramon yoki bir guruh qahramonlarning ichki dunyosi va tashqi voqealarni o'z ichiga oladi. Hakimning dostonlari, voqea va lavhalar orqali insoniy tuyg'ularni, jamiyatdagi muammolarni va tabiat bilan munosabatlarni o'ziga xos tarzda ifodalaydi. Bu dostonlar, odatda, bir nechta qismlarga bo'linadi, har bir qism o'z ichiga muayyan mazmun va rivojlanishni oladi. Shu tariqa muallif o'quvchilarni chuqurroq fikrlashga va mavzuni kengroq tushunishga jalb etadi.

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THE INFLUENCE OF FOLKLORE: MYTHICAL WOMEN IN RUSSIAN CULTURE

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Annotation: This article explores the profound impact of folklore on the representation of mythical women in Russian culture. She delves into the rich tapestry of Russian folklore, exploring how legendary female figures such as Baba Yaga, Vodyanitsa and Rusalki embody cultural values, social norms and the complexity of femininity. Through a comprehensive analysis of various folk tales, songs, and oral traditions, the article highlights the dual nature of these mythical women, who often serve as educators and antagonists, reflecting women's multifaceted roles in society. The article also examines the historical context in which these folklore narratives originated, how they evolved over time, and their importance in modern Russian literature and art. Analyzing the symbolism associated with these signs, the article reveals how they challenge and reinforce gender stereotypes, providing insight into the cultural psyche of Russia. In addition, the debate influences the contemporary interpretations of femininity by these legendary women and their exposure in contemporary media. Ultimately, this article focuses on highlighting the enduring heritage of folklore in shaping perceptions of women in Russian culture, emphasizing the need for a deeper understanding of these narratives in historical and modern contexts.

Key words: folklore, mythical women, Russian culture, baba yaga, vodyanitsa, rusalki, gender roles, cultural identity, oral traditions, female archetypes, symbolism, feminine mystique, historical context, contemporary literature, gender stereotypes, cultural psyche, narrative analysis, folktales, mythology, women's representation Russian folklore teems with powerful female figures who have shaped the cultural imagination for centuries. From the mysterious forest witch Baba Yaga to the ethereal Swan Maiden, these mythical women embody the complex relationship Russians have historically maintained with femininity, nature, power, and the supernatural. Far from being mere relics of a pre-modern past, these folkloric figures continue to influence contemporary Russian art, literature, music, and even social attitudes. This article explores the most significant mythical women in Russian folklore and traces their enduring impact on Russian cultural identity and expression.

Perhaps no female figure in Russian folklore is more recognizable or complex than Baba Yaga. Typically depicted as an old crone with iron teeth who flies in a mortar and pestle and lives in a hut standing on chicken legs, Baba Yaga represents the quintessential ambiguous feminine force in Russian mythology.

Unlike the one-dimensional witches of Western European fairy tales, Baba Yaga defies simple categorization. Depending on the tale, she may appear as a dangerous cannibal who threatens to eat the protagonist, or as a wise woman who offers crucial magical assistance to those who show proper respect and complete her impossible tasks. This duality reflects Russian folk culture's nuanced

understanding of feminine power as both nurturing and destructive. In tales like "Vasilisa the Beautiful," Baba Yaga tests the heroine's worthiness before providing

magical aid, while in others, she actively seeks to devour those who cross her path. Her moral ambiguity suggests a pre-Christian understanding of nature itself-unpredictable, potentially dangerous, yet also a source of wisdom and power.

Baba Yaga's hut, which stands at the border between the human world and the realm of magic and spirits, positions her as a liminal figure—a guardian of thresholds and transitions. The ritualistic language used by those approaching her domain ("Little hut, little hut, stand with your back to the forest and your front to me") underscores her role as gatekeeper between worlds. This liminality extends to her physical representation; neither fully human nor spirit, she embodies the in-between spaces in Russian cosmology. Her association with both death and transformation links her to life cycle transitions, particularly initiation rites and coming-of-age experiences.

Baba Yaga's influence extends far beyond traditional folklore. In Russian literature, she appears in sophisticated reinterpretations by writers from Alexander Pushkin to Viktor Pelevin. Soviet and post-Soviet animation has featured her prominently, most notably in the beloved film "Domovyonok Kuzya." Contemporary Russian artists continue to explore her symbolism, and she has entered global popular culture through video games, comics, and Western adaptations of Russian folklore. Most significantly, Baba Yaga has become a psychological archetype in Russian culture—representing the wisdom that comes through confronting fear and the transformative potential of engaging with the natural world's darker aspects. Her enduring appeal lies in her refusal to conform to patriarchal expectations of femininity, making her a complex symbol of female autonomy and power.

If Baba Yaga represents ambiguous feminine power, Vasilisa (appearing in various tales as Vasilisa the Beautiful, Vasilisa the Wise, or Vasilisa the Brave) embodies the idealized Russian heroine—combining beauty, intelligence, and moral fortitude.

Unlike male heroes who often succeed through physical prowess, Vasilisa triumphs through cleverness, patience, and resourcefulness. In her encounters with Baba Yaga and other supernatural forces, she demonstrates the value of wisdom over brute strength, representing a distinctly feminine approach to heroism in Russian folklore. Her character suggests that even in patriarchal Russian society, there was cultural recognition of female intelligence as a powerful force. The epithet "Wise" attached to her name in many variants emphasizes that her mental capacities, not merely her beauty, define her worth.

In the tale "Vasilisa the Beautiful," the heroine receives a magical doll from her dying mother that helps her accomplish impossible tasks. This matrilineal transfer of power and knowledge represents the importance of female ancestral wisdom in Russian folk tradition. The doll, animated by maternal blessing, symbolizes the continuing presence of female ancestors in guiding new generations.

Contemporary Russian culture continues to celebrate Vasilisa's attributes. In Soviet and post-Soviet children's literature, she became a model of the capable, independent girl who succeeds through education and cleverness. Russian feminist writers have reclaimed her as a proto-feminist figure who achieves autonomy through intelligence rather than marriage to a powerful man. Films like Aleksandr Rou's "Vasilisa the Beautiful" (1939) and various theatrical adaptations have kept

her story alive in popular culture, while her attributes are often referenced in naming practices and everyday expressions about female competence.

The Rusalka—a water spirit typically depicted as the ghost of a young woman who died by drowning or suicide—represents one of the darker aspects of femininity in Russian folklore.

Rusalki (plural) are often portrayed as beautiful young women with long, flowing green hair and pale skin who emerge from lakes and rivers during the Rusalki Week (a summer folk holiday). According to legend, they lure young men to the water with their enchanting voices and appearance, only to drown them in a deadly embrace. As the spirits of "unclean" dead—often unmarried pregnant women, suicide victims, or those who died before their natural time—

Rusalki represent societal anxiety about female sexuality and women who exist outside patriarchal structures. Their association with water connects them to primordial feminine symbolism, with water representing both life-giving potential and dangerous depths.

Traditional Russian village culture included rituals specifically designed to appease the Rusalki during their active season. Young women would leave offerings of garments in trees near water and perform special songs and dances to protect the community from their malevolent influence. These practices reveal the deep psychological impact these figures had on traditional communities and demonstrate how mythological beings functioned as mechanisms for addressing societal fears about female autonomy and sexuality.

The tragic figure of the Rusalka has inspired numerous works of Russian art, most notably Alexander Dargomyzhsky's opera "Rusalka" (1856) and Pushkin's unfinished dramatic poem of the same name. Painters like Ivan Kramskoi and Konstantin Makovsky created haunting visual interpretations of these water spirits, emphasizing their otherworldly beauty and sorrowful nature. In contemporary Russian culture, the Rusalka continues to appear in literature, film, and popular music as a symbol of doomed love and the consequences of societal restrictions on female autonomy. Her enduring presence suggests a continuing cultural fascination with the dangerous aspects of female power and the tragic consequences of patriarchal control.

While Father Frost (Morozko or Ded Moroz) himself is a central figure in Russian winter mythology, many folk tales feature his daughter as a significant female character who rewards kindness and punishes cruelty.

In the classic tale "Morozko," a kind-hearted stepdaughter is sent into the winter forest to die by her cruel stepmother. There she encounters Father Frost, who tests her patience and politeness. When she responds with courtesy despite freezing, she is rewarded with rich gifts. When her stepsister later attempts to receive the same rewards but responds rudely, she is punished with freezing death. This tale establishes a connection between feminine virtue, endurance, and natural justice. The winter landscape-traditionally gendered as masculine in Russian culture-becomes the setting where feminine moral qualities are tested and rewarded.

The daughter of Frost, sometimes called Snegurochka (Snow Maiden) in later adaptations, represents the gentler aspects of winter's power. Her association with snow's beauty rather than its deadly cold creates a complementary feminine aspect to the winter mythology that dominates northern Russian folklore.

The Snow Maiden character evolved significantly during the 19th century, most notably in Nikolai Rimsky-Korsakov's opera "Snegurochka" (1882) based on Alexander Ostrovsky's play. In this adaptation, she becomes a tragic figure whose desire to experience human love causes her to melt when touched by warm emotion-creating a powerful metaphor for the perceived incompatibility between female emotional expression and power. During the Soviet period, the Snow Maiden was incorporated into New Year celebrations as the granddaughter and helper of Ded Moroz (the Russian Santa Claus figure), transforming her from a potentially tragic figure into a nurturing, child-friendly symbol of winter's beauty. This transformation demonstrates how folkloric figures adapt to changing cultural needs while maintaining core symbolic associations.

The tale of the Frog Princess (Tsarevna Lyagushka) presents one of the most complex transformative female figures in Russian folklore, reversing Western expectations by featuring a female rather than male enchanted animal.

In this tale, a prince is forced to marry a frog, only to discover that his amphibian bride transforms at night into a beautiful and talented woman named Vasilisa. When he prematurely burns her frog skin, she is forced to return to the magical realm, and he must undergo difficult

trials to win her back. Unlike Western tales where male characters are enchanted and passive female figures break the spell, the Frog Princess actively manages her dual nature until external interference disrupts her transformation process. This agency suggests a distinctly Russian perspective on feminine power as something that operates according to its own rules and timing, rather than male expectations.

The Frog Princess demonstrates extraordinary abilities in traditional female domains—her bread baking, weaving, and dancing surpass all human competitors. This representation elevates domestic female arts to the realm of magic, suggesting that traditionally feminine skills contain power that deserves recognition and respect.

The Frog Princess tale continues to resonate in contemporary Russian culture through numerous adaptations in literature, animation, and theater. The image of a powerful woman whose true nature remains hidden from superficial observation speaks to ongoing cultural negotiations about female identity and societal expectations. Modern feminist interpretations emphasize the princess's autonomy in managing her transformation and the prince's need to prove himself worthy of her rather than the reverse, reclaiming the tale as a narrative of female empowerment disguised within traditional marriage structures. Less known internationally but significant in Slavic agricultural communities is Poludnitsa (or Poluden)—the female spirit who appears in fields at midday during the hottest summer days.

The mythical women of Russian folklore represent a rich and complex cultural inheritance that continues to shape Russian identity and artistic expression. From the ambiguous power of Baba Yaga to the cosmic guardianship of the Zorya sisters, these figures embody diverse aspects of feminine experience and power that have remained relevant across centuries of social change. Their persistence suggests that despite historical patriarchal structures in Russian society, the culture has always maintained space for recognition of female power, wisdom, and agency—if often in forms displaced into the supernatural realm. As contemporary Russians continue to negotiate gender roles and national identity in a rapidly changing world, these mythological female figures provide valuable cultural resources for imagining diverse possibilities of feminine being. The enduring influence of these mythical women demonstrates how folklore functions not merely as historical artifact but as living cultural inheritance that continues to evolve through reinterpretation and adaptation. In their ambiguity, power, and resistance to simple categorization, the mythical women of Russian folklore continue to captivate the imagination and influence cultural expression in Russia and beyond.

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ECOCRITICAL NARRATIVES IN "THE ROAD" BY CORMAC MCCARTHY

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Abstract. The paper explores Cormac McCarthy's "The Road" (2006), a post-apocalyptic novel that examines the relationship between human survival and the ravaged environment in a world where ecological collapse has led to the near extinction of human life, through an ecocritical lens, analyzing how writer's portrayal of a desolate, post-apocalyptic world challenges readers' perceptions of nature, environmental degradation, and human responsibility. Drawing on ecocritical theories, the paper investigates themes of environmental collapse, human-nature interactions, and the ethical implications of ecological neglect.

Keywords: ecocriticism, environmental collapse, McCarthy, survival.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqola Kormak Makkartining 2006-yilda yozilgan "Yo'l" nomli post-apokaliptik romaniga ekotanqidiy nuqtai nazardan yondashadi, unda yozuvchi dunyo ekologiyasining halokatli o'sishining natijasida inson hayotining deyarli yo'qolishiga olib kelgan bir muhitda insonning omon qolishga bo'lgan munosabatini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu maqolada yozuvchining post-apokaliptik, buhronli dunyoni tasvirlashi insonlar va tabiat orasidagi munosabatlar, ekologik zararlanish va inson mas'uliyatiga oid o'ylarmizga qaytadan ishora qiladi. Ekotanqidiy nazariyalardan foydalangan holda, maqola ekologik halokat, inson-tabiat o'zaro ta'siri va ekologik nemaxsuslikning etik jihatlarini tadqiq qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekotanqid, ekologik halokat, Makkarti, omon qolish.

Аннотация. В данной статье роман Кормака Маккарти «Дорога» (2006), изображающий постапокалиптический мир, разрушенный экологической катастрофой и приведший к почти полному исчезновению человечества, рассматривается с точки зрения экокритики, вызывающей у читателей переосмысление концепций природы, экологического разрушения и человеческой ответственности. Основываясь на экокритических теориях, статья анализирует такие темы, как экологическое бедствие, взаимодействие человека и природы, а также этические последствия экологической безответственности.

Ключевые слова: экокритика, экологическое бедствие, Маккарти, выживание.

Introduction. Cormac McCarthy's "The Road" presents a haunting vision of a post-apocalyptic world where human life struggles to survive amidst an environment rendered hostile and barren by unspecified environmental calamity. Published in 2006, the novel explores themes of survival, father-son relationships, and the persistence of hope in the face of extinction. Yet, at its core, "The Road" is an ecocritical text that critically examines the consequences of environmental degradation and the ethical responsibility humans bear in shaping the planet's future. Through the bleak and often desolate portrayal of a destroyed ecosystem, McCarthy critiques humanity's role in the ecological crisis while questioning the

sustainability of modern society. This paper applies an ecocritical framework to “The Road”, exploring how the novel engages with environmental concerns and offers commentary on the human-nature relationship. By investigating key themes of ecological collapse, the role of nature as both antagonist and salvation, and the ethical dilemmas posed by environmental destruction, this paper seeks to uncover the deeper environmental messages embedded within McCarthy's narrative.

Literature Review. Ecocriticism, as an interdisciplinary field, focuses on the relationship between literature and the environment. Buell [1] and Glotfelty [2] have highlighted the importance of analyzing literary texts through an ecological lens to uncover how narratives shape, reflect, and critique human interaction with the natural world. In recent years, post-apocalyptic literature has become an important site for ecocritical analysis, as it allows for an exploration of the consequences of ecological neglect. In the context of McCarthy's works, several scholars have explored his treatment of nature and its metaphysical implications. Thus, Heise analyzes McCarthy's depiction of desolate landscapes and suggests that McCarthy's vision of post-apocalyptic America critiques capitalist exploitation of the environment [3]. Moreover, Osteen have argued that McCarthy's post-apocalyptic landscapes serve as a warning about the consequences of ecological indifference [5]. “The Road” has been studied extensively for its portrayal of environmental collapse. Price contends that McCarthy's writing reflects a deep ecological consciousness, where the environment is both a metaphor for human isolation and a character in its own right [6]. Moreover, Robinson emphasizes McCarthy's unique use of language to convey ecological suffering, arguing that the novel functions as a moral commentary on the environmental crisis of the 21st century [7]. These critical perspectives inform the present analysis, as they point to the narrative's engagement with human responsibility, ecological fragility, and survival ethics in a climate-damaged world.

Results. In “The Road”, nature plays a central role in shaping the narrative and characters. The novel's setting is an environment that has been irrevocably altered by ecological collapse, leaving behind a world devoid of biodiversity and life. McCarthy's description of the environment as a barren wasteland of ash and decay functions as both a literal and metaphorical representation of the destructive consequences of human environmental negligence. The barren landscapes echo the desolate inner lives of the characters, who are stripped of societal structures and left to survive in a world where nature has turned hostile.

One significant finding of this study is McCarthy's use of nature as an antagonist. The environment is not merely a passive backdrop but an active force that challenges human survival. As the novel progresses, the natural world becomes increasingly inhospitable. Forests are gone, animals are extinct, and the air is thick with soot, leaving the father and son to grapple with the harsh realities of a dying planet. The survivalist ethos portrayed in the novel highlights the fragility of human existence in the face of environmental collapse.

The ethical dimension of “The Road” emerges in the interactions between the father and the son, as they traverse this devastated world. Their journey reflects the tension between survival and morality in a world where the rules of civilization no longer apply. The father, despite the overwhelming need to protect his son, continually struggles with the moral implications of their survival, suggesting that ecological and ethical dilemmas are inseparable. The novel's emphasis on the necessity of maintaining "the fire" (a symbol of hope and humanity) suggests that even in a world devoid of natural resources, the preservation of ethical values remains essential.

Discussion. McCarthy's novel highlights the interdependence between human survival and ecological integrity, presenting nature not as something to be controlled or dominated, but as a force that must be respected and cared for. The environmental collapse depicted in "The Road" serves as a cautionary tale about the dangers of unchecked environmental exploitation and ecological degradation. Through the representation of a world where the land has been rendered inhospitable, McCarthy critiques the consequences of humanity's historical disregard for the planet's fragility.

The figure of the father, who constantly emphasizes the need to "carry the fire" (a symbol of hope, morality, and human integrity), can be seen as a metaphor for the ethical responsibility humanity bears in relation to the environment. This moral imperative, however, is complicated by the dire conditions of the post-apocalyptic world. The father's internal struggles reveal the tension between survival instincts and moral duties, asking whether it is possible to preserve ethical values when the world itself has descended into chaos.

Moreover, the relationship between the father and son emphasizes the need for intergenerational responsibility. The father's desire to protect his son and pass on the "fire" suggests that there is hope for future generations, even in the darkest of times. However, this hope is contingent upon the moral choices that humanity makes in relation to the environment, underlining the intergenerational implications of ecological degradation.

Conclusion. "The Road" serves as a profound ecological critique of contemporary society's exploitation of the natural world. Through its bleak portrayal of environmental collapse, McCarthy invites readers to reflect on the consequences of unsustainable ecological practices and the ethical obligations humanity has toward the planet. The novel's depiction of nature as both an antagonist and a site of human resilience underscores the fragility of ecological systems and the need for a profound shift in human behavior.

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BADIIY ASAR TILINI LINGVISTIK NUQTAYI NAZARDAN O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada badiiy asar tilini lingvistik nuqtayi nazardan o'rganish masalasi yoritilgan bo'lib, o'zbek adabiyotshunosligida bu yo'nalishda olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlil qilinadi. Muallif badiiy tilning xalq tili bilan uzviy bog'liqligini, unda xalqchilik ruhi ustunligini ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, Abdulla Qodiriy, Alisher Navoiy, Abdulla Qahhor, G'afur G'ulom kabi yirik adiblarning badiiy tildan foydalanish mahorati

misolida soʻz estetikasi, uslubiy aniqlik va ifoda goʻzalligi tahlil etiladi. Tadqiqotda filolog olimlarning badiiy asar tili haqidagi nazariy qarashlari ham oʻrganilib, til estetikasi nafaqat adabiyotda, balki kundalik nutqda ham muhim kommunikativ va estetik ahamiyat kasb etishi taʼkidlanadi. Maqola badiiy asar tilini oʻrganishning metodik jihatlarini ochib berib, uni taʼlim jarayoniga tatbiq etishning ahamiyatini asoslaydi.

Kalit soʻzlar: badiiy asar tili, til estetikasi, lingvistik tahlil, uslub, adabiy til, xalq tili, ifoda goʻzalligi, badiiy nutq, oʻzbek adabiyoti, filologik tadqiqot.

Abstract: This article explores the study of the language of literary works from a linguistic perspective, analyzing the scholarly research conducted in this field within Uzbek literary studies. The author emphasizes the close connection between literary language and the spoken national language, highlighting the dominant spirit of folk expression in artistic texts. The article examines the linguistic mastery and stylistic precision of prominent Uzbek writers such as Abdulla Qodiriy, Alisher Navoi, Abdulla Qahhor, and Gʻafur Gʻulom, focusing on the aesthetics of language, stylistic clarity, and expressive beauty. It also discusses the theoretical views of philological scholars on the language of literary works, underlining that linguistic aesthetics serves not only a literary but also a communicative and aesthetic function in everyday speech. The paper further reveals the methodological aspects of studying literary language and substantiates its importance in the educational process.

Keywords: language of literary works, linguistic aesthetics, linguistic analysis, style, literary language, folk language, expressiveness, artistic speech, Uzbek literature, philological research.

Muammoning oʻrganilishi bilan aloqador boʻlgan adabiyotlarni kuzatish shuni koʻrsatadiki, badiiy asar tilini oʻrganish filolog olimlarimiz tomonidan ancha salmoqli tarzda amalga oshirilgan. I.Qoʻchqortoyev adabiyotshunoslik yoʻnalishidagi tadqiqotlarni oʻzbek klassik adabiyoti, oʻsha paytlarda “demokratik adabiyot” deb nomlanadigan adabiyot, hamda yigirmanchi asr badiiy adabiyotining tilini oʻrganishga bagʻishlangan ilmiy ishlarni tasnif qilgan edi [1].

Bevosita sarlavhaga badiiy asar tili bilan bogʻliq muammolar chiqarilmagan boʻlsada, tadqiqotlarda bu masalaga oid ancha salmoqli va jiddiy mulohazalar bildirilganini koʻrish mumkin. Ayniqsa, yirik adiblarimiz (Abdulla Qodiriy, Choʻlpon, Abdulla Qahhor, Oybek, Maqsud Shayxzoda, Gʻafur Gʻulom, Hamid Olimjon, Zulfiya, Pirimqul Qodirov, Odil Yoqubov) ning bu boradagi fikr-mulohazalari alohida diqqat va eʼtiborga molikdir.

Izzat Sulton, A.Gʻulomov, A.Ahmedov, X.Doniyorov, S.Mirzayev, Gʻ.Abdurahmonov, Sh.Shoabdurahmonov, I. Qoʻchqortoyev, Q.Samadov, B.Umurqulov va boshqa olimlarning maqola va tadqiqotlarida muammoning oʻziga xos yechim va talqinlari berilgan.

“Soʻz estetikasi” degan kitob bevosita badiiy asar tili tahliliga ba-gʻishlangani bilan eʼtiborli. Unda nazariy jihatdan toʻgʻri boʻlgan bir fikr alohida taʼkidlanadi: “Koʻpincha til estetikasi haqida gap ketganda, faqat muayyan yozuvchining tili atrofida fikr yuritiladi. Estetikani faqat badiiy asarlar tiligagina xos, undan tashqarida til estetikasi haqida gapirish mumkin emas deb qarash notoʻgʻridir. Chunki til estetikasining asosi nutqning sifatiga, qandayligiga suyanadi. Jonli soʻzlashuvda ham, koʻpincha, fikrning qanday ifodalanayotganligiga eʼtibor beriladi. Ana shu eʼtibor bilanoq til oʻzining kommunikativ funksiyasi bilan birgalikda estetik funksiyasini ham namoyon qiladi. Demak, nafaqat badiiy asarda, balki undan tashqarida ham til oʻzining estetik funksiyasi bilan ishtirok etishi mumkin”[1]. Umuman, filolog olimlarimizning bunday ishlari metodika sohasida ham amaliy yordam bera oladi. Ularning asosiy fikr va xulosalarini taʼlim-tarbiya jarayoniga tatbiq etish metodist olimlarimizning muhim vazifalari boʻlib turibdi.

Badiiy asar tili xalq tili (jonli til, adabiy til)ga asoslanganligi sabab unda xalqchilik ruhi doimo ustun turadi. Badiiy asarlarda turli jamiyatlardagi hamma tabaqalarning tiliga duch kelar ekanmiz, ularning tilida qo‘llanilgan har bir so‘z tushinarli bo‘lishi talab qilinadi.

Abdulla Qodiriy asarlari tahlili bilan shug‘ullangan olimlarimiz adib mahoratining asosiy ko‘rsatkichi uning tili ekanligini e‘tirof etishadi. “Abdulla Qodiriy asarlaridagi sehrli jozibaning omillaridan biri uning tilidir” [3], - deb yozadi akademik M. Qo‘shjonov. Buning sabablari esa shunday izohlanadi: “Adib so‘zlarni nihoyatda aniq tanlaydi, bu so‘zlardan nihoyatda aniq jumlar tuzadi va bu aniq jumlar qahramonlar holatiga tegishli aniq maqsadlarda ishlatiladi” [4]. Nazarimizda, muallifning quyidagi fikrlari ham nihoyatda o‘rinlidir: “Shu kunlarda uchraydigan chiyralgan, buralgan, sun‘iy tarzda murakkablashtirilgan, aniq maqsadga bo‘ysundirilmagan so‘z va iboralar qo‘llaydigan qalamkashlar Abdulla Qodiriydan o‘rnak olsalar chakki bo‘lmas edi” [5].

Hamid Olimjon Alisher Navoiy haqida gapirarkan, uning badiiy tildan foydalanish mahoratiga alohida baho beradi. Uning «har bir bayti quyma bir haykaldan iborat bo‘lgan»ligini ta’kidlaydi. Adibning haqli e‘tiroficha, «O‘z til xazinasining boy va kengligi e‘tibori bilan Navoiy, Shekspir, Pushkin va Firdavsiylar qatorida turadikim, uning asarlariga lug‘at yozganlarning hech biri bu xazinaning nihoyasiga yeta olmaganlar»[6].

Hamid Olimjon Abdulla Qahhor prozasi haqida gapirib shunday yoza-di: “So‘nggi yillarda nasrchilik bobida ancha yosh talantlar yuzaga chiqdi. Bunda o‘zining katta hunarmandligi va go‘zal tili bilan yosh hikoyanavis Abdulla Qahhorning xizmati katta. Bizning yozuvchilarimiz ichida Abdulla Qahhor qadar boy va chiroyli tilga ega bo‘lgan yozuvchi yo‘q deyish mumkin. Abdulla Qahhorni, xususan tilda, boshqa yozuvchilardan ajratib turgan narsa esa uning mavzuni va turmushni chuqur o‘rganishidan, puxta va jiddiy ishlashidan, voqealarning ichidan asosiy nuqtalarini topa bilishidan, kerakni keraksizdan, zarurni nozarurdan ajrata bilganidan, o‘z hunarining texnikasini egallaganidan keladi” [2]. Demak, ijodkorlarning o‘zlari ham badiiy asar tiliga alohida e‘tibor bilan qaraganlarini qayd etish o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Yirik munaqqid va adabiyotshunos O. Sharafiddinov G‘afur G‘ulom asarlarining mashhur va manzurligini uning badiiy tili bilan bog‘liq holda ko‘rganida to‘la haq edi: “U har qanday she‘rida, hatto eng ko‘tarinki ohangda yozilgan she‘rlarida ham, tilning sodda bo‘lishiga, xalq tiliga yaqinlikka, jonli so‘zlashuv ohanglariga ega bo‘lishga intildi. Natijada, uning she‘rla-ri yanada kuchliroq hayotiylik kasb etdi, ularning ta’sir kuchi ortdi” [2].

Adabiy asarni yaxlit jonli qiluvchi asosiy kuch badiiy tildir. U shuning uchun ham badiiy asarning hamma hujayralarida yashaydi. Shu hujayralarning tirikligini ta’minlaydi. Agar asarni millonlab so‘z hujayralarni tashkil topishini ko‘z o‘ngimizga keltira olsak, g‘oya va mazmun ham, obraz va xarakter ham, syujet va kompozitsiya ham qo‘yinki, badiiy asarning hamma unsurlari ham ana shu asosida bunyod bo‘ladi.

Taniqli yozuvchi Tohir Malik Abdulla Qodiriy asarlarining jozibasini birinchi navbatda uning tilida ko‘radi: “Abdulla Qodiriyning adabiy til borasidagi mahoratlarini durlar xazinasiga qiyoslashimiz mumkin. Adibning hikoyalari, felyetonlari, hajviyalarini o‘qisangiz, bunga o‘zingiz ham guvoh bo‘lasiz. Toshpo‘lat tajang bilan Kalvak mahzumning so‘zlari bir-biridan tubdan farq qiladi. Yozuvchi “Ovsar” taxallusi bilan bir felyeton yozsa, “Dumbul” taxallusida yozilgan hangomadan farqlanib turadi. Bilmagan odam bu ikki asarni ikki odam yozgan, deb o‘ylashi ham mumkin” [2].

Mumtoz adabiyot namoyandalari asarlaridagi til xususiyatlari tahlili ham tadqiqotchilar e‘tiborida bo‘lgan Bu jihatdan akad. A.Rustamovning Navoiy asarlari tili ustidagi kuzatishlari tahsinga loyiq. Olimning yozishicha, “til juda katta ma’rifiy ahamiyatga ega... Ammo tilning ahamiyati bu bilan tugamaydi. Tilning badiiy imkoniyati cheksiz...”. Biz prof.

S.Ashirboyevning “Qutbning “Xusrav va Shirin” dostoni va o‘zbek adabiy tili” kitobchasini alohida ko‘rsatishni istardik. Unda adabiy til va sheva munosabatlari, doston tilining fonetik, morfologik xususiyatlari ancha keng ta’riflab berilgan [4].

Mazkur yo‘nalishdagi eng jiddiy ishlardan biri sifatida M.Yo‘ldoshovning “Badiiy matn va uning lingvopoetik tahlili asoslari” kitobini ko‘rsatish mumkin. Unda to‘g‘ri ko‘rsatilganidek, “Adabiy asarning san‘at darajasiga ko‘tarila olishi uning lisoniy tarkibi va asar muallifining badiiy ifoda balog‘atiga bog‘liq ekanligi shubhasiz. Shunday ekan, har qanday adabiy asarning mohiyatini xolis baholamoq uchun, eng avvalo, uning lisoniy tarkibining o‘ziga xosligini tahlil etish lozim” [4]. Muallifning o‘z oldiga “badiiy matn tahlil qilish metodologiyasi, lingvopoetik tahlil tamoyillari va usullari, tahlil tiplari”ni o‘rganish vazifasini qo‘yganligi muhimdir. Unda badiiy matnning o‘ziga xosligi, uning tarkibi, tuzilishi, semantikasi, ifoda yo‘sini haqidagi kuzatish va mulohazalari faqat tilshunoslar uchun emas, amaliyotchi o‘qituvchilar uchun ham katta metodik yordam vazifasini bajara oladi.

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SHARQ OILAVIY AN‘ANALARI MISOLIDA ARAB VA O‘ZBEK MADANIYATINING UZVIYLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada arab va o‘zbek oilalaridagi madaniy qadriyatlar, oila tizimi va tarbiyaviy an‘analar taqqoslanadi. Tadqiqot ikki jamiyatning oilaviy tuzilishi, qarindoshlik munosabatlari, ayol va qizlarning roli hamda farzand tarbiyasi tizimini o‘rganishga qaratilgan. Maqolada madaniy o‘xshashliklar va farqlar, tarixiy va sotsiokulturologik kontekstda tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, oila qadriyatlari va tarbiya jarayonlarining jamiyatning ijtimoiy-madaniy barqarorligiga ta’siri ko‘rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Sharq oilasi, arab madaniyati, o‘zbek oilasi, tarbiya, ayol va qizlarning roli, oilaviy qadriyatlar, qarindoshlik munosabatlari, madaniy o‘xshashlik.

Sharq mamlakatlarida oila qadriyatlari avloddan-avlodga uzatiladigan ijtimoiy va madaniy kod sifatida shakllangan. Arab va o‘zbek oilalarida esa oila nafaqat ijtimoiy birlik, balki ma’naviy qadriyatlarni saqlash va tarbiyalash muassasasi sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Arab oilalarida oilaviy tizim ko‘pincha kengaytirilgan bo‘lib, ota-ona, bolalar, amakivachcha, tog‘a-birodar va boshqa qarindoshlar o‘rtasida chuqur ijtimoiy bog‘lanishlar mavjud [1]. Shu bilan birga, o‘zbek oilalarida ham qarindoshlik munosabatlari qadimiy an‘analarga asoslangan bo‘lib, oila a‘zolari bir-birining ma’naviy va moddiy qo‘llab-quvvatlash tizimini shakllantiradi [4].

Ikkala jamiyatda ham ayol va qizlarning tarbiyadagi roli muhim ahamiyatga ega. Arab oilasida ayollar farzandlarni diniy va axloqiy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalaydi, o'zbek oilalarida esa ayol nafaqat tarbiyachi, balki oilaning ma'naviy uyg'unligini saqlovchi markaz sifatida qaraladi [3].

Shuningdek, farzand tarbiyasi, qarindoshlik munosabatlari va gender rollarining shakllanishi ikki madaniyat o'rtasida qiziqarli o'xshashlik va farqliklarni ko'rsatadi. Bu jihat, nafaqat madaniyatshunoslik, balki sotsiologiya va pedagogika nuqtai nazaridan ham tadqiq etishga loyiqdir.

Maqoladan ko'zlangan maqsad shuki: arab va o'zbek oilalaridagi tarbiyaviy tizim, qadriyatlar va madaniy o'xshashliklarni tahlil qilish, shuningdek, oilaviy an'analar orqali jamiyatdagi uzviylikni ko'rsatishdir. Tadqiqot quyidagi vazifalarni amalga oshiradi:

1. Arab va o'zbek oilalarining tarbiyaviy tizimini o'rganish;
2. Ayol va qizlarning tarbiyadagi roli va vazifalarini taqqoslash;
3. Qarindoshlik munosabatlari va madaniy qadriyatlarning o'xshash va farqli jihatlarini aniqlash;
4. Oilaviy an'analar va qadriyatlar orqali jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy barqarorlikni tahlil qilish.

Metodologiya

Ushbu tadqiqot taqqoslovchi va sotsiokulturologik metodlar asosida olib borildi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi - arab va o'zbek oilalaridagi tarbiyaviy tizim, ayol va qizlarning roli hamda qarindoshlik munosabatlarini o'rganish va ularni madaniy kontekstda taqqoslash.

Tadqiqotda quyidagi yondashuvlar ishlatildi:

1. Adabiyotlar tahlili - arab va o'zbek oilalariga oid ilmiy maqolalar, tarixiy manbalar, madaniyatshunoslik va pedagogik tadqiqotlar o'rganildi [3].
2. Taqqoslash metodi - ikki jamiyatning oilaviy tizimlari, tarbiya jarayoni va qadriyatlar o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlar aniqlandi.
3. Sotsiokulturologik tahlil - oiladagi ayol va qizning roli, qarindoshlik munosabatlari va madaniy qadriyatlarning jamiyatdagi uzviyligi o'rganildi.

Tadqiqotda asosiy e'tibor oilaviy qadriyatlar va tarbiyaviy yondashuvlarga qaratildi. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar, gender rollarining yangilanishi va madaniy moslashuv tahlil qilindi [1].

Natijalar

Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, arab va o'zbek oilalari ko'plab madaniy o'xshashliklarga ega, shu bilan birga ayrim farqlar ham mavjud:

1. Oila tuzilishi: Arab oilalari ko'pincha kengaytirilgan bo'lib, ota-ona, bolalar va qarindoshlar birgalikda yashaydi. O'zbek oilalarida esa asosiy ijtimoiy birlik - yaqin qarindoshlar bilan yashovchi kichik oiladir [2].

2. Ayol va qizlarning roli: Ikkala jamiyatda ham ayol oilaning tarbiyaviy markazi sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Arab oilalarida ayol diniy va ma'naviy tarbiyada faol ishtirok etsa, o'zbek oilalarida u bolalarning ijtimoiy va axloqiy rivojlanishida markaziy shaxs hisoblanadi [3].

3. Qarindoshlik munosabatlari: Arab oilalarida qarindoshlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy bog'lanishlar yanada keng va rasmiy bo'lsa, o'zbek oilalarida ular mehr-oqibat va axloqiy qadriyatlar asosida shakllanadi [4].

4. Tarbiyaviy tizim: Ikkala madaniyatda ham tarbiya diniy va madaniy qadriyatlar bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Qizlar tarbiyasi oilaning ma'naviy barqarorligi va jamiyatdagi axloqiy uyg'unlikni ta'minlashda muhim hisoblanadi.

5. Madaniy o'xshashliklar: Arab va o'zbek oilalarida ayol va qizlarning tarbiyadagi roli, qarindoshlik aloqalarining ahamiyati, va oilaning jamiyatdagi barqarorlikdagi funksiyasi o'xshashdir [5].

6. Farqlar: Arab oilalarida diniy qadriyatlar va an'anaviy ijtimoiy tuzilmalar kuchliroq aks etgan bo'lsa, o'zbek oilalarida ijtimoiy moslashuv va shaxsiy o'zaro aloqalar muhimroq rol o'ynaydi.

Shuningdek, zamonaviy davrda globalizatsiya va ta'limning kengayishi ikki madaniyatdagi oilaviy qadriyatlarning moslashuvchanligini oshirgan. Arab oilalarida ta'lim va ijtimoiy faoliyatga ayollarning jalb etilishi tarbiyaning yangicha shakllanishini talab qilmoqda, o'zbek oilalarida esa urbanizatsiya va mehnat faoliyati oilaviy rollarni qayta shakllantirmoqda.

Taqqoslovchi tahlil shuni ko'rsatadiki, arab va o'zbek oilalarida oilaviy qadriyatlar, tarbiya jarayoni va ayol-qizning roli uzviy tarzda bog'langan. Asosiy xulosalar quyidagilar:

1. Ayol va qizlarning roli: Ikkala madaniyatda ham ayol oilaning tarbiyaviy markazi, qizlar esa kelajak onalari sifatida tarbiyalanadi.

2. Qarindoshlik munosabatlari: Arab va o'zbek oilalarida qarindoshlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy va ma'naviy bog'lanishlar oilaning barqarorligini ta'minlaydi.

3. Madaniy o'xshashlik va farqlar: O'xshashlik - tarbiya tizimi, qadriyatlar va oilaning ijtimoiy funksiyasi; Farq - arab oilasida diniy va an'anaviy qadriyatlar kuchliroq, o'zbek oilasida shaxslararo iliqlik va moslashuv muhimroq.

4. Zamonaviy tendensiyalar: Globalizatsiya va ta'limning kengayishi oilaviy qadriyatlarning yangicha talqinini keltirib chiqarmoqda.

Shu bilan arab va o'zbek oilalari o'rtasidagi madaniy uzviylik va ixtiloflarning muvozanati o'rganildi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, oilaviy an'analar va qadriyatlar jamiyatning ma'naviy barqarorligini saqlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

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COMPARISON OF WOMEN, SOCIETY, AND LOVE IN KODIRIY'S "OTKAN KUNLAR" AND AUSTEN'S "PRIDE AND PREJUDICE"

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Abstract. This paper compares "Bygone Days" (called O'tkan kunlar in Uzbek) by Abdulla Kodiriy and "Pride and Prejudice" by Jane Austen, focusing on their treatment of tradition, individual agency and the role of women in society. Both novels depict protagonists

navigating societal expectations, particularly in matters of love and marriage. Set in distinct historical and cultural contexts-19th century Turkestan and Regency-era England, both novels criticize rigid social structures and explore the struggle between personal desires and societal norms. This analysis highlights key thematic parallels and differences, shedding light on how literature from different cultures addresses the universal human experience.

Key words: literature, literary meaning, context, emotions, current literary themes, societal norms, women's role, tradition, love, individual agency.

Literature is the voice of the human soul, the fruit of thought, and the reflection of the spirit. It is the expression of society, just as speech is the expression of man. The President of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, has also defined literature in this way: "Literature is one of the most important pillars of human spirituality. It is the heart of the nation, it reflects the spirituality of the people. In today's complex time, we must use the powerful influence of literature to reach people's hearts and inspire them toward noble goals" [1]

There are such literary works that, no matter how many articles we write about them. We always feel the urge to write more. Two such masterpieces are "Bygone Days" (1926) and "Pride and Prejudice" (1813). Every literary work serves as a mirror reflecting the society of its time. These two world-renowned works explore love, conformity to societal expectations and universal themes, making them timeless for future generations.

Both novels employ symbolism to reflect societal values and character development. Otabek's chapan and doppi symbolize loyalty, while Kumush's tragic fate illustrates how societal pressure crushes personal dreams. Similarly, Lydia Bennet's elopement reveals the fragility of women's reputation in 19th century England. We would really like to emphasize this as well. Thought Kumush submitted to traditions and accepted her fate, deep in her heart, deep in her heart, the fire of freedom and happiness burned. Her patience and devotion shone like a bright star, even in the face of the hardest trials. She might have brought about positive changes in society and left his mark on it. It is no surprise that she contributed to the spiritual elevation of human relationships.

Love is one of the strongest forces that ensures human freedom. The love between Otabek and Kumush is not just an emotional connection but also a reflection of the struggle between tradition and modernity. Similarly, Elizabeth Bennet remained true to her beliefs and values, refusing to yield to society's constraints but instead facing them with courage. Her intelligence and independent thinking transformed love from more emotion into a rational choice built on equality and respect. In its turn, Elizabeth Bennet symbolizes how personal and social expectations crash in some points. Ultimately, the freedom of will and options have to be left as a deciding factor for each person.

In early 19th century England, women had little autonomy in marriage, as economic stability often dictated their choices. Elizabeth Bennet's decision to marry based on love rather than financial security was a bold act of defiance for her time. Let us briefly talk about marriage during this period. According to statistical data in Regency-era England (1811-1820) the average marriage age for women was 20-23. However, upper-class girls often married earlier (18-19) due to societal pressure. And also, in England, before 1870, married women had no right to own property; any wealth they inherited automatically belonged to their husbands.

In Turkestan, the average marriage age for girls was 14-16, and they had no say in choosing their husbands, as marriages were arranged by their parents. But in Turkestan, women technically had property rights, but in practice, most had little economic independence. This contrast explains the societal pressures surrounding marriage in both novels and helps contextualize Elizabeth Bennet's desire for independence and Kumush's lack of agency in financial matters.

In *Bygone Days*, parents prioritize their social reputation over their children's happiness. As a result, Kumush and Otabek's love is sacrificed to societal norms. In this novel portrays fate as predetermined, with individuals bound to the rules of society. In *Pride and Prejudice*, parental influence varies. Mr. Bennet values his daughters' happiness, while Mrs. Bennet focuses solely on finding wealthy suitors. This contrast reflects two different perspectives on marriage and parental control in that era. And it suggested that with personal determination, one can resist social pressure and shape their destiny. This contrast highlights the differences in Eastern and Western societal structure regarding personal agency. As Fyodor Dostoevsky mentioned: "Man wants to be free, but he also fears his freedom".

In *Bygone Days*, Otabek and Kumush dream of freedom but remain trapped by societal norms. *Pride and Prejudice*, however, shows that internal courage can break social constraints. These two renowned novels, based on various social issues, explore themes of love and duty, the clash of traditions, national identity, social stratifications, marriage and personal growth. *Bygone Days* primarily depicts historical transformations and fixed social idioms, while *Pride and Prejudice* focuses on moral values.

It should be also noted that distinguished by its unique style and narrative approach, *Bygone Days* reflects romantic and cultural aspects, as well as, personal and political transformations. In *Pride and Prejudice*, personal relationships take precedence with social satire, dialogue and irony playing a central role.

Let us briefly discuss some of the most notable characters. Kumush, described as unmatched in loyalty, embodies a woman who endured the hardship of her time and remained faithful to her love. Her powerful words serve as proof of this: "I cannot sacrifice my happiness for the wishes of others". [3]

Meanwhile, Elizabeth, in *Pride and Prejudice*, a woman who values her own destiny, is portrayed as ambitious, strong and patient- an iconic literary figure known worldwide. Elizabeth's statement: "My courage always rises with every attempt to intimidate me" [4]

It is a testament to her determination and bravery. It is worth emphasizing Simone de Beauvoir's remark that 'One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman'. This aligns with Kumush and Elizabeth Bennet's experiences. Both women are shaped by societal expectations, yet they strive to define themselves on their own terms. *Bygone days* shows that no matter how sincerely and moderately a person tries to find solutions to societal challenges, society itself remains unyielding and intensifies its resistance.

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Annotatsiya: Oddiy askar – adabiyot va tarix chorrahasidagi obraz. Bu obraz dunyo adabiyotining eng qadimiy va eng dolzarb obrazlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek adabiyotida oddiy askar obrazi talqinlari haqida fikr yuritiladi

Kalit so'zlar: *timsol, birinchi jahon urishi, oddiy askar, tarix, troya, jangovarlik, realistik obraz, psixologik tasvir, hayot va o'lim.*

Abstract: The ordinary soldier – a figure at the crossroads of literature and history. This figure is considered one of the oldest and most relevant images in world literature. This article discusses interpretations of the image of the ordinary soldier in Uzbek literature.

Keywords: *symbol, First World War, ordinary soldier, history, Troy, militancy, realistic image, psychological depiction, life and death.*

Аннотация. Образ простого солдата находится на пересечении литературы и истории. Этот образ считается одним из самых древних и в то же время наиболее актуальных в мировой литературе. В данной статье рассматриваются интерпретации образа простого солдата в узбекской литературе.

Ключевые слова: символ, Первая мировая война, простой солдат, история, Троя, воинственность, реалистический образ, психологическое описание, жизнь и смерть

Kirish - XX asr insoniyat tarixida nafaqat taraqqiyot va ilm-fanning ulkan yutuqlari bilan, balki mislsiz fojealar – ikki jahon urushi bilan ham esda qoldi. Bu urushlar nafaqat siyosiy chegaralarni o'zgartirdi, balki butun dunyo xalqlarining ruhiy hayotiga, ma'naviy qiyofasiga ham beqiyos iz qoldirdi. Jahon urushlari insoniyat tarixida ilgari bunday ko'rilmagan talafotlarni keltirib chiqardi: millionlab begunoh odamlarning hayoti yarim yo'lda so'ndi, shaharlar vayronaga aylandi, madaniy merosning ko'p qismi yo'qoldi.

Birinchi jahon urushi insoniyatga o'zining achchiq saboqlarini bergan bo'lsa, Ikkinchi jahon urushi bu fojealarni yanada chuqurlashtirdi. Uzoq yillar davom etgan janglar insoniy qadriyatlarini poymol qildi, mehnatkash xalqlarni og'ir sinovlarga soldi. Urush maydonlarida kechgan janglar faqat askarlar taqdirini emas, balki butun boshli xalqlar hayotini o'zgartirib yubordi. Millionlab insonlar qochqinlikka yuz tutdi, ocharchilik, qashshoqlik va og'ir ruhiy iztiroblar odamlarning ongiga o'chmas darajada muhrlandi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili - Shu o'rinda O'tkir Hoshimovning "Tushda kechgan umrlar asarida" aytib o'tilgan quyidagi so'zlar e'tiborga molik: "Urushda g'olib va baxtli podshoh, g'olib va baxtli qo'shin, g'olib va baxtli davlat, g'olib va baxtli tuzum bo'lishi mumkin. Lekin g'olib va baxtli odam bo'lmaydi. Negaki urush odamni odam o'ldirishga majbur qiladi. Odam o'ldirgan odam esa hech qachon baxtli bo'la olmaydi" [1] [1:288]

Eng og'riqli jihati shundaki, bu urushlarning talafotlari faqat moddiy yo'qotishlar bilangina cheklanib qolmadi. Ular insoniyat ruhiyatiga ham katta zarba berdi. Urush yillarida bolaligining eng beg'ubor lahzalaridan ayrilgan avlod voyaga yetdi, onalar farzandlaridan, farzandlar esa ota-onalaridan judo bo'ldi. Insoniyat o'zini o'z qo'li bilan vayronaga aylantirayotganligini anglab yetdi. Bu davrda yaratilgan ko'plab badiiy asarlar urushning naqadar dahshatli oqibatlarini, inson qalbiga solgan og'ir jarohatlarini tasvirlab berdi. Shu bois jahon urushlari tarixga faqat yovuz kuchlarning to'qnashuvi sifatida emas, balki insoniyatning o'z taqdirini o'zi qanday o'zgartira olishi, qanday vayronaga ham, qanday bunyodkorlikka ham qodir ekanligining achchiq dalili sifatida kirdi. Bu fojealardan insoniyat katta saboq oldi: tinchlikning qadrini, inson hayotining bebaho ekanligini chuqur anglashga majbur bo'ldi. Bugungi avlod uchun jahon urushlari tarixdan o'rganiladigan saboq, tinchlik va hamjihatlik esa eng ulug' ne'matdir.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi - Maqolada o'zbek adabiyotida oddiy askar muamosi talqinlari muhokama qilinadi. Askar obrazi orqali nafaqat jang maydonlaridagi qahramonliklar, balki insoniyatning eng qiyin sinovlaridagi ma'naviyati, qahramonligi, zaifliklari va umidlari ifodalanishi tasviri o'rganild

Tahlillar va natijalar - O'zbek adabiyotida Ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida yaratilgan oddiy askar obrazi xalqning mardligi, fojialarga bardosh berish qobiliyati va mustaqillik, ozodlik yo'lidagi kurashining yorqin timsoli bo'lib qoldi. O'zbek adabiyotida Ikkinchi jahon urushi davri asarlari xalqning og'ir sinovli taqdirini, askarning qiyofasi orqali butun millatning qahramonligini yoritishga xizmat qildi.

G'afur G'ulomning "Sen yetim emassan" asari[2:15] front ortidagi bolalar hayotini tasvirlar ekan, unda oddiy askar obrazi bevosita ko'rinmasa-da, ularning ota-onasi, Vatan himoyachilari qiyofasida mavjuddir. Bu asar orqali oddiy askar – xalq farzandi – millatning ertangi kuni uchun kurashayotgan, ammo uning orqasida qoldirgan oilasi ham buyuk sinovlardan o'tayotganini ko'ramiz. G'afur G'ulom she'riyatida askar obrazi vatanparvarlik va insoniyatsevarlikni mujassam etgan. G'afur G'ulom askar obrazini insoniy qadriyatlarining tashuvchisi sifatida ko'rsatadi.

Hamid Olimjonning she'riyati[3:35] ham urush davrida xalqni ruhlantirish, askarlarning matonatini madh etishga xizmat qilgan. Uning qahramonlik va sadoqat ruhidagi she'rlarida oddiy askar millat g'ururining timsoli sifatida ulug'lanadi.

Uyg'un va Mirtemir ijodida ham urush mavzusi keng o'rin oldi. Ularning she'r va dostonlarida askarning Vatanga sadoqati, qo'rqmasligi, dushmanga qarshi mardona kurashi tasvirlanadi. Mirtemirning "O'zbekiston" [4:62] she'ri Vatan va uning farzandlari - oddiy askarlarning botirligini kuylaydi.

Urushdan keyingi yillarda esa adabiyotda askar obrazi yangicha talqin topa boshladi. Odil Yoqubovning "Ulug'bek xazinasini", "Adolat manzili" kabi asarlari tarixiy mavzuda bo'lsa-da, ulardagi qahramonlar ruhiyati urushni ko'rgan avlodning kechinmalariga hamohangdir.

Ozod Sharafiddinov va boshqa adabiyotshunoslarning ta'kidlashicha, urush davrida yaratilgan asarlarda oddiy askar timsoli qahramonlik, xalqona sadoqat va Vatanni sevish fazilatlarini bilan uyg'unlashgan. Keyingi yillarda esa bu obraz xalqning tinchlikdagi mehnatkash timsoliga aylangan.

Demak, o'zbek adabiyotida Ikkinchi jahon urushi davri va keyingi yillarda oddiy askar obrazi:

- urush maydonidagi jasorat timsoli;
- front ortidagi oilaning tayanchi;
- xalqning birligi va sabr-toqatini ifodalovchi;

tinchlik davrida esa mehnatkash, Vatan ravnaqiga hissa qo'shuvchi qiyofa sifatida keng talqin qilindi.

Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalarida[5:28] frontdagi oddiy jangchilarning hayoti, ularning qiyin kunlari, ammo shu bilan birga umidlari va orzulari aks etadi. Uning "Og'riq tishlar" hikoyasida askarning jang maydonida ham o'z oilasi va yurtini eslashi, uning oddiy odam ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Tog'ay Murod asarlarida urushning og'ir izlari va askarning psixologik portreti chuqur yoritilgan. Uning "Otamdan qolgan dalalar" romanida urushdan qaytgan askarning tinch hayotga moslashishdagi qiyinchiliklari, psixologik travmalari haqqida so'z yuritiladi.

O'tkir Hoshimovning "Tushda kechgan umrlar"[1:54] romanida urush va tinchlik davridagi oddiy askar hayoti, uning oilaviy baxti va dardlari haqqida hikoya qilinadi. Bu asarda askar obrazi orqali urushning oddiy odamlar hayotiga ta'siri ko'rsatiladi. Uning bu

romani xalqning urushdan keyingi og‘ir hayoti, oddiy insonlarning sabr-toqati va bardoshini ochib beradi.

Zamonaviy adabiyotda ayol askar obrazi ham muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Bu obraz orqali nafaqat jangovar vazifalar bajarayotgan ayol, balki urush sharoitida ona, xotin, singil sifatidagi murakkab psixologik holatlari aks etadi. Ayol askar obrazi gender rollari, jasorat va noziklik paradokslarini ifodalaydi. Ayol kishi askar obrazida tasvirlangan asarlar adabiyotda o‘ziga xos ahamiyat kasb etadi. Odatda urush mavzusi erkaklarning qahramonligi, ularning sabr-toqati va jasorati orqali ko‘proq ochib beriladi. Biroq ayolning ham askar sifatida tasvirlanishi badiiy asarga alohida ta‘sirchanlik, chuqurlik va samimiylilik baxsh etadi. Chunki ayol obrazi nafaqat jangchi, balki mehribon, hayotbaxsh, onaona timsoli sifatida ham o‘quvchida ikki tomonlama tasavvur uyg‘otadi. Shunday asarlarda ayol askar obrazi bir vaqtning o‘zida ham jangchi, ham ona, ham sevuvchi, ham sabrli inson sifatida ko‘rsatiladi.

Jahon adabiyotiga nazar tashlansa, Ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida ayollar qator erkaklar bilan birga frontda jang qilgani, hayotini qurbon qilgani ko‘plab asarlarda aks etgan. Masalan, sovet adabiyotida Zoya Kosmodemyanskaya singari tarixiy shaxslar obrazlari qahramonlik ramzi sifatida badiiy asarlarda o‘z ifodasini topgan. Aleksandr Fadeyevning “Yosh gvardiya” asarida ayol qahramonlarning vatanparvarligi, matonati va qo‘rqmasligi asosiy g‘oyani boyitgan. G‘arb adabiyotida ham ayolning jangchi sifatida maydonga chiqishi haqida yozilgan asarlar mavjud. Bu obrazlarda ayolning sabr-bardoshi, or-nomusi, yurt va oila uchun o‘zini qurbon qilishi o‘quvchini larzaga soladigan darajada tasvirlanadi.

O‘zbek adabiyotida ham Ikkinchi jahon urushi mavzusiga oid asarlarda ayol askar obrazi alohida o‘rin tutadi. Aslida o‘zbek adabiyotida ayolning urush davridagi jasorati ko‘pincha ramziy talqinda ifodalangan: ba‘zan u haqiqatan qurol ko‘tarib jang qiluvchi qahramon bo‘lsa, ba‘zan esa orqa frontdagi mehnat fidoyisi sifatida askarlikka xos fazilatlarni mujassamlashtirgan holda tasvirlanadi. Saida Zunnunovaning she‘rlari, Zulfiya ijodi, urush davri adabiy matbuotida chop etilgan ko‘plab asarlar buning yorqin dalilidir. Bu asarlarda ayol askarning qudrati, matonati, yurakdagi orzulari va ayni paytda ayollikka xos nozikligi badiiy ranglar bilan ifodalanadi.

Ayol askar obrazining badiiy talqinida bir necha muhim jihatlar mavjud. Avvalo, qahramonlik va fidoyilik eng asosiy yo‘nalish sifatida ko‘zga tashlanadi. Ayol qahramon jang maydonida erkaklar bilan teng kurashadi, uning jasorati hech qanday istehzoga yoki shubhalarga sabab bo‘lmaydi. Ikkinchi jihat – mehribonlik va insoniylikdir. Erkak askarlar ko‘proq qahramonlikning tashqi belgisi, jangovar ruh orqali gavdalantirilsa, ayol askar obrazi ko‘pincha insoniylik, hayotga bo‘lgan ishonch, mehr va ona ruhi bilan uyg‘unlashtiriladi. Uchinchidan, ayol obrazi orqali urushning fojialari yanada chuqurroq yoritiladi. Chunki ayol qahramon ko‘pincha sevgidan, oiladan, farzand orzusidan ayrilgan, ammo shu yo‘qotishlariga qaramay Vatanni himoya qilishga bel bog‘lagan inson sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ayol kishi askar obrazida tasvirlangan asarlar urush mavzusini yanada ta‘sirchan, yanada insoniy qirralar bilan boyitadi. Bu obrazlar orqali nafaqat qahramonlik, balki mehr, sabr-toqat, hayot uchun kurashish, insoniy qadriyatlarga sadoqat singari fazilatlar ham ochib beriladi. Ayol askar obrazi adabiyotda ikki xil ruhiyatni uyg‘otadi: bir tomondan, ayolning erkaklar qatori jang maydonida ko‘rsatgan jasorati o‘quvchini hayratga soladi, ikkinchi tomondan esa, uning qalbidagi mehribonlik va insoniylik urush fojiasini yanada chuqur his qilishga majbur etadi. Shu bois ayol askar obrazlari adabiyot tarixida nafaqat qahramonlik timsoli, balki insoniylik va mehribonlik ramzi sifatida ham abadiy yashab kelmoqda.

O‘zbek xalqi tarixida ayollar har doim matonat, sabr-toqat va fidoyilik timsoli sifatida e‘zozlanib kelgan. Bu fazilatlar Ikkinchi jahon urushi yillarida yanada yorqinroq namoyon bo‘ldi. Erkaklar safda jang qilayotgan bir paytda, ko‘plab ayollar ham frontga otlanib,

erkaklar bilan yelkama-yelka vatan mudofaasida qatnashdilar. Ularning orasida Zebo G'aniyeva kabi jasur qizlar ham bor edi. U snayper sifatida frontda xizmat qilib, o'zining qahramonligi bilan nafaqat o'zbek xalqining, balki butun Sovet Ittifoqi askarlarining faxriga aylangan. Bunday jasoratli qizlarning ismi tarix sahifalariga oltin harflar bilan yozilgan bo'lsa, ularning siymosi adabiyotimizda ham yorqin obraz sifatida aks etdi.

Adabiyotda ayol askar obrazi ko'pincha ikki tomonlama yondashuv asosida gavdalanadi. Bir tomondan, ular jangchi, vatanparvar, mard va jasur insonlar sifatida tasvirlanadi. Qurol ko'tarib, dushmanga qarshi kurashayotgan ayol qiyofasi o'quvchini hayratga soladi, qalbida iftixor tuyg'ularini uyg'otadi. Ikkinchi tomondan esa yozuvchilar ayollarning mehribon, nozik, insoniy his-tuyg'ular bilan yo'g'rilgan qiyofasini ham unutmaydilar. Shu bois urush maydonida ham ayol qalbining tabiiy sezgirligi, onalik tuyg'usi, sevgi va sadoqatga intilishi tasvirlanadi. Bu ikki qutb obrazni yanada boyitadi, unga hayotiy kuch beradi.

Ayol askar obrazi, avvalo, urushning naqadar shafqatsiz ekanini ko'rsatadi. Chunki tabiatan mehribonlik va tinchlik timsoli bo'lgan ayollarni ham qurol ko'tarishga majbur etgan kuch - bu urushning o'zi. Shunday qilib, yozuvchilar bunday obraz orqali urushning fojeasini yanada chuqurroq ochadilar. Ayolning frontda halok bo'lishi yoki yaralanishi, uning ortida qolgan onasi, farzandi yoki yaqinlarining iztiroblari asarda katta ruhiy yuk vazifasini bajaradi.

O'zbek adabiyotida urush mavzusiga bag'ishlangan ko'plab asarlarda ayol askar siymosi uchraydi. Ular ko'pincha qahramonlik va fidoyilik timsoli bo'lsa-da, shu bilan birga urushning insoniy taqdirarni izdan chiqaruvchi, ayollar hayotini ham ostin-ustun qiluvchi dahshatli hodisa ekanini ifodalaydi. She'riyatda ayol askar qahramonligi ko'proq lirizm bilan boyitilib, ona vatanga sodiqlik, mehr va or-nomus timsolida madh etiladi. Nasrda esa ularning jang maydonidagi jasorati, oddiy hayotdagi armonlari, taqdiridagi iztiroblar realistik talqinda ifodalanadi.

Shunday qilib, Zebo G'aniyeva singari tarixiy shaxslar obrazi o'zbek adabiyotida ham o'z aksini topib, ayol askar qiyofasini yanada yuksak darajada gavdalantirdi. Bu obraz bugun ham yosh avlodni Vatanga muhabbat, jasorat, sadoqat va matonat ruhida tarbiyalashda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ayolning jangchi sifatida tasvirlanishi – bu bir tomondan xalqning mardligi va sabr-toqatini, ikkinchi tomondan urushning naqadar shafqatsiz va ayanchli ekanini badiiy ifodalashning yorqin vositasidir.

Turli madaniyatlarda askar obrazi turlicha talqin qilinadi. Sharq adabiyotida askar ko'pincha fidoyilik, itoatkorlik va mardlik ramzi sifatida tasvirlansa, G'arb adabiyotida ko'proq individualistik va tanqidiy yondashuv ustunlik qiladi. Ko'p millatli armiyalar haqidagi asarlarda etnik xilma-xillik va uning urushdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi. Sharq adabiyotida askar ko'pincha fidoyilik, itoatkorlik, yurt va din yo'lida jonini tikkan mard sifatida talqin etiladi. Masalan, Alisher Navoiy asarlarida jangchi obrazlari ko'proq yuksak axloqiy g'oya - adolat, xalqni himoya qilish, yovuzlikka qarshi kurash ramzi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Turk xalqlar dostonlarida (masalan, "Alpomish" yoki "Manas") jangchi – vatanparvar, qahramon, xalqi uchun o'zini qurbon qilishga tayyor shaxsdir. Sharqona talqinda askar – bu shaxsiy manfaatini emas, balki jamoaning saodati va yurtning sha'nini himoya qiluvchi timsol.

Xulosa - Xulosa qilib aytganda, Sharqda askar - fidoyilik va itoatkorlik ramzi, G'arbda - shaxsiy kechinmalar, urushning absurdligi va insoniy fojialar markazida turadigan obrazdir. Ko'p millatli armiyalarda esa askarning obraziga xalqlar o'rtasidagi birdamlik, madaniy xilma-xillik va umumiy maqsad yo'lida kurashish g'oyasi qo'shiladi. Bu xilma-xillik askar obrazini universal, shu bilan birga har bir madaniyatga xos tarzda boyitib kelmoqda.

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РОЛЬ ЦВЕТООБОЗНАЧЕНИЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА

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Аннотация: В данной статье освещен феномен, именуемый "картина мира", является таким же древним, как сам человек. Картина мира представляет собой центральное понятие концепции человека, выражает специфику его существования.

Ключевые слова: Феномен, картина мира, изобразительное искусство, отображение мира, лингвистика

Феномен, именуемый "картина мира", является таким же древним, как сам человек. Создание первых "картин мира" у человека совпадает по времени с процессом антропогенеза. Тем не менее, реалия, называемая термином "картина мира", стала предметом научно-философского рассмотрения лишь в недавнее время. При характеристике картины мира необходимо различать три важных взаимосвязанных, но не тождественных явления: 1) реалию, именуемую термином "картина мира"; 2) понятие "картина мира", воплощающее теоретическое осмысление этой реалии; 3) термин "картина мира". Картина мира представляет собой центральное понятие концепции человека, выражает специфику его существования. Понятие картины мира относится к числу фундаментальных понятий, выражающих специфику человеческого бытия, взаимоотношения его с миром, важнейшие условия его существования в мире. Картина мира есть целостный образ мира, который является результатом всей активности человека. Она возникает у человека в ходе всех его контактов и взаимодействий с внешним миром. Это могут быть и бытовые контакты с миром, и предметно - практическая активность человека. "Отпечатки" картины мира можно обнаружить в языке, в жестах, в изобразительном искусстве, музыке, ритуалах, этикете, вещах, мимике, в поведении людей. [1,123 стр.] Картина мира формирует тип отношения человека к миру - природе, другим людям, задаёт нормы поведения человека в мире, определяет его отношение к жизни. Язык непосредственно участвует в двух процессах, связанных с картиной мира. Во-первых, в его недрах формируется языковая картина мира, один из наиболее глубоких слоёв картины мира у человека. Во-вторых, сам язык выражает и эксплицирует другие картины мира человека, которые через посредство специальной лексики входят в язык, принося в него черты человека, его культуры. При помощи языка опытное знание, полученное отдельными индивидами, превращается в коллективное достояние, коллективный опыт. Языковая картина мира - это отражённый средствами языка образ сознания - реальности, модель интегрального знания о концептуальной системе представлений, репрезентируемых языком. Языковую картину мира, так же принято интерпретировать как отражение обиходных, обывательских представлений о мире. Идея наивной модели мира состоит в следующем: в каждом естественном языке отражается определённый способ

восприятия мира, навязываемый в качестве обязательного всем носителям языка. Вопрос концептуализации мира языком при помощи слов, очень важен. Специфика варьирования составляет существенную часть специфики языковых картин мира. Первый фактор - природа. Природа - это, прежде всего внешние условия жизни людей, которые по-разному отражены в языках. Человек даёт названия тем животным, местностям, растениям, которые ему известны, тому состоянию природы, которое он ощущает. Природные условия диктуют языковому сознанию человека особенности восприятия, даже таких явлений, каким является восприятие цвета. Обозначение разновидностей цвета часто мотивируется семантическими признаками зрительного восприятия предметов окружающей природы. С тем или иным цветом ассоциируется конкретный природный объект. [2,94стр.] В разных языковых культурах закрепились собственные ассоциации, связанные со цветовыми обозначениями, которые и совпадают в чём-то, но и в чём-то отличаются друг от друга. Второй фактор - культура. "Культура - это то, что человек не получил от мира природы, а привнёс, сделал, создал сам". Результаты материальной и духовной деятельности, социально-исторические, эстетические, моральные и другие нормы и ценности, которые отличают разные поколения и социальные общности, воплощаются в различных концептуальных и языковых представлениях о мире. Любая особенность культурной сферы фиксируется в языке. Также языковые различия могут обуславливаться национальными обрядами, обычаями, ритуалами, фольклорно-мифологическими представлениями, символикой. Культурные модели, концептуализированные в определённых наименованиях, распространяются по миру и становятся известны даже тем, кто не знаком с культурой того или иного народа. Этой проблеме в последнее время посвящается очень много специальных работ и исследований. Что касается третьего фактора - познания, то следует сказать, что рациональные, чувственные и духовные способы мировосприятия отличают каждого человека. Способы осознания мира не идентичны для разных людей и разных народов. Об этом говорят различия результатов познавательной деятельности, которые находят своё выражение в специфике языковых представлений и особенностях языкового сознания разных народов [3,141 стр].

При оценке картины мира следует понимать, что она - не отображение мира и не окно в мир, а она является интерпретацией человеком окружающего мира, способом его миропонимания. "Язык - отнюдь не простое зеркало мира, а потому фиксирует не только воспринятое, но и осмысленное, осознанное, интерпретированное человеком" . Это означает, что мир для человека - это не только то, что он воспринял посредством своих органов чувств. Напротив, более или менее значительную часть этого мира составляют субъективные результаты осуществлённой человеком интерпретации воспринятого. Поэтому говорить, что язык есть "зеркало мира", правомерно, однако это зеркало не идеально: оно представляет мир не непосредственно, а в субъективном познавательном преломлении сообщества людей. Мысль о том, что создание картины мира или картины реальности является необходимым моментом жизнедеятельности человека, развивал А. Эйнштейн: "Человек стремится каким-то адекватным способом создать в себе простую и ясную картину мира для того, чтобы оторваться от мира ощущений, чтобы в известной степени попытаться заменить этот мир созданной таким образом картиной" . Параллельно с разработкой понятия картины мира в рамках науки, картина мира изучалась в культурологических и лингвосомиологических работах. Специфика языковой концептуализации мира нагляднее всего представлена в том, что называют особенностями в языковом членении действительности, что можно объяснить этнонациональными различиями когнитивных мировосприятий. Языки различаются способом выделения значений, самим способом восприятия и

осмысления мира. Эта идея в различных ипостасях и версиях развивалась во всех ключевых эпохах новейшей истории лингвистики.

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HALIMA SHE'RLARI VA BADIY SAN'ATLAR

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Annotatsiya: Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodiyotini o'rganish. Uning she'rlarida jozibadorlik, inson ruhiyatini erkinlik va komillikka yetaklovchi g'oyalar timsoli. She'rlarda qo'llanilgan badiiy san'at vositalarining qo'llanilishi va ta'sir ko'lami. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodiyotining, adabiyot, insoniyat va kamolatga hissasi.

Kalit so'zlar: ruhiyat, gulqaychi sohibasi, ichimdagi sher, tashbeh san'ati, uyg'un tuyg'ular, tirik so'z.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается творческое наследие Халимы Худойбердиевой. В её поэзии отражаются образы идей, ведущих человеческую душу к свободе и совершенству, а также очарование поэтического слова. Анализируется использование художественно-образительных средств и их влияние на восприятие читателя. Особое внимание уделяется вкладу поэтессы в развитие литературы, духовности и человеческого самосовершенствования.

Ключевые слова: душевность, владычица поэзии, внутренний лев, искусство сравнения, гармоничные чувства, живое слово.

Abstract: The article explores the creative legacy of Halima Khudoyberdiyeva. Her poetry embodies the charm of artistic expression and the ideas that guide the human soul toward freedom and perfection. The study analyzes the use and impact of poetic devices in her works. Special attention is given to the poet's contribution to literature, humanity, and spiritual development.

Keywords: spirituality, mistress of poetry, inner lion, art of simile, harmonious feelings, living word.

Adabiyotimizda o'chmas iz qoldirgan shoiramiz Halima Hudoyberdiyeva o'zining yuksak did sohibasi, uyg'oq vijdoni va tirik she'rlari bilan shuhrat qozongan. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva o'zbek zamonaviy she'riyatining eng nozik, eng sezgir vakillaridan biridir. Uning she'rlari ayol qalbining dard va orzularini, inson ruhiyatining eng yashirin qatlamlarini badiiy jilolantirishi bilan ajralib turadi. Shoira nafaqat so'z ustasi, balki milliy g'urur, ma'naviyat va erkin fikr timsoli sifatida ham adabiyotimiz tarixida chuqur iz qoldirdi. Uning shoirlik missiyasi - so'z orqali insonni uyg'otish, ruhiyatga ta'sir etish va komillikka yetaklashdir. Halima Xudoyberdiyeva ijodi o'zbek adabiyotida "ayol lirikasi"ning yangi ufqlarini ochdi. Shoira har bir she'rida o'z qalbini, o'z ruhini so'zga aylantiradi. Uning satrlari orqali nafaqat shaxsiy dard, balki umuminsoniy tuyg'ular, vatan sog'inchi va erkinlikka

intilish tarannum etiladi. Shu bois Halima she'rlari o'quvchini o'ylashga, sezishga va his etishga majbur qiladi - u fikrni emas, tuyg'uni boshqaradi.

Shoiraning adabiyot maydoniga kirib kelishi o'zbek she'riyatida yangi ruh, yangi dard va yangi ohangni yuzaga chiqardi. Ijodining asosiy tamoyili - "so'z orqali o'zlikni anglash va boshqalarga anglatish" edi. U o'z she'rlarida shaxsiy kechinmalar orqali jamiyat ruhiyatini ko'rsatadi: ayolning dardini Vatan dardi bilan, ona ko'ksini millat ko'ksining iztirobi bilan qovushtiradi.

BATAMOM UYG'ON SAM... [1. 123-bet]

Turayotgan qushga

O'xshayman juda,

Qushlarga o'xshayman

Uyg'onayotgan.

Ba'zi tomirlarim

Hali uyquda,

Ba'zi tomirlarda

Qonlarim qotgan.

"Batamom uyg'on sam" nomli she'rida o'zining va jamiki insoniyatning vijdoni uyg'onishi intizorlik bilan kutayotgani kuylanmoqda. Shoira o'zini uyqudan uyg'onayotgan qushga o'xshatadi, endigina uyg'onayotgan qush. Ba'zi tomirlarida qon qotib qolgan, harakatsiz va ba'zilari esa Hali hamon uhlamoqda. Har bir misra uyg'oqlikka, vijdon va qalbni go'yo oppoq qog'ozdek asramoqqa undaydi.

Xas-xashaklar bilan

Sudralib yurib,

O'qlik orzusida

Ketib borar yoy.

O'zim-cha nelardur

G'udranib yurib,

Guldayin umrimni,

Bermoqdaman boy.

She'rning qolgan misralari ham alohida e'tiborga molik. Tiriklik bor ekan banda arzimagan, qadri xashakchalik muammolar bilan hayot yo'llarida boradi. Yo'l oxirida aniq bir maqsad haqiqiy mo'minlik, lekin nolishlar, betoqatlik va qanoatsizlik-la bo'lib guldayin umrimni boy berayotganligini ta'kidlamoqda. Aslini olganda hech bir dard alam, muammo yo'qki umrimizdan azizroq bo'lsa?. Insonlar dunyo uchun emas, dunyo insonlar uchun yaratildi va jonni fido aylamoq, umrni fido aylamoq arzimas.

Har bir misrada yaqqol seziladiki insonlarni komillik sari yetaklaydigan, ruhiyat va qalbini poklaydigan so'zlar tizib chiqilgan. Bunday mahorat har kimda ham shakklanavermaydi. Satrlarga saralangan so'zlar albatta Halimaning gulqaychisidan o'tgan. She'rlarda g'alizlik paydo qiladigan so'zlar kiritilmagan, eng saralari jamlangan. O'qiguvchi qalbini to'lqinlantiradigan, jumbushga keltiradigan, hissiyotlar bo'ronini yuvib yoboradigan so'zlarning barchasini o'z she'rida to'plashni uddalay olgan. Yozuvchi O'tkir Hoshimov yozganidek "har bir she'r shoirdan farzand kabi tug'uladi ". [2] Halima xalqimizga va adabiyot ahllariga komillikka yetaklovchi farzandlardan minglab dunyoga keltirdi axir.

O'zimcha kimningdir

G'amini yedim,

Kimningdir kuniga

Yuribman yarab.

Batamom uyg'onib

Ololsam edi,

*Uchib ketarmidim
Ko'klarga qarab.*

Yozuvchi Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshev shoiramizni "Halima Xudoyberdiyeva – yuragida yo'lbars o'kirib, sirdan mayin jilmaygan, yirik shaxsiyat egasi edi. Ammo shunday kuchli tuyg'ularini ham o'zbek ayoliga xos tarzda, andisha bilan aytardi" [3]deya ta'riflaydi. Halima yuragida shunday ulkan yo'lbars borki u hayqiradi, yozuvchini to'lg'ontiradi, tunlari uyqu bermaydi, yozishga undaydi. Ayollik nafasat va didi orqali nozik ammo tig'day o'tkir qalami orqali hayqiriqlarni noziklik bilan yoritib beradi.

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THE ROLE OF LITERARY TEXTS IN TEACHING CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. The study investigates the role of literary texts in teaching cultural competence within English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Literature, as an authentic representation of cultural values, social norms, and historical perspectives, provides learners with insights into the English-speaking world that extend beyond linguistic structures. The article examines how the integration of novels, short stories, and poetry fosters intercultural awareness, empathy, and interpretative skills among students. Drawing on theoretical frameworks of intercultural competence and communicative approaches to teaching, the study demonstrates that literary texts not only enrich vocabulary and grammar knowledge but also expose learners to diverse worldviews. The research concludes that systematic use of literature in EFL instruction enhances students' cultural sensitivity and equips them with tools for more effective intercultural communication.

Keywords: literary texts, cultural competence, EFL teaching, intercultural communication, communicative approach.

Introduction. Teaching a foreign language is not merely the transfer of grammatical rules and vocabulary items; it is also an immersion into the cultural contexts where the language lives and functions. Language and culture are inseparable, and understanding one without the other results in limited communicative competence. For this reason, the integration of literature into EFL instruction has received increasing attention. Unlike simplified didactic texts, authentic literary works embody cultural nuances, historical experiences, and social dynamics that cannot be easily conveyed by conventional textbooks.

This article explores the importance of literary texts in developing cultural competence among EFL learners. By analyzing how novels, short stories, and poetry contribute to language acquisition and intercultural understanding, the study provides theoretical and practical insights into their pedagogical application.

Literature Review. The role of literature in language teaching has been widely discussed in applied linguistics. Kramsch (1993) argued that literature offers a "third place" where learners negotiate between their own culture and the target language culture, developing intercultural competence. Abrams (1997) defined cultural competence as the ability to interact effectively with people from different cultural backgrounds, a skill that literature naturally fosters by exposing learners to authentic cultural content.

Collie and Slater (1987) emphasized that literature enhances language learning by stimulating imagination and personal engagement, which motivates learners to interact with the text beyond surface-level comprehension. More recently, Paran (2008) and Carter (2015) have noted that literature develops not only linguistic competence but also interpretative and critical thinking skills.

These studies suggest that the use of literature in EFL teaching is a multidimensional tool, connecting linguistic development with cultural awareness.

Methodology. This study employs a qualitative approach based on document analysis and pedagogical case studies. The primary sources include literary texts commonly used in EFL classrooms, such as short stories by O. Henry, novels by Jane Austen and Charles Dickens, and selected modern works. The analysis focuses on how these texts contribute to the development of learners' cultural competence, as evidenced in existing teaching practices and research findings.

Results and Discussion. The analysis demonstrates that literary texts serve as powerful instruments for teaching cultural competence in EFL contexts. First, literature provides learners with authentic exposure to the social norms, values, and traditions of English-speaking cultures. For example, novels such as *Pride and Prejudice* offer insights into social hierarchy, gender roles, and etiquette of 19th-century Britain, while contemporary works highlight modern cultural issues such as diversity, identity, and globalization. By engaging with these cultural narratives, learners develop a deeper understanding of the contexts in which the English language operates.

Second, literature fosters empathy and intercultural awareness. Through characters and their experiences, students are invited to view the world from different perspectives, which enhances their ability to relate to people from diverse cultural backgrounds. Short stories, with their condensed form, are particularly effective for classroom use, as they encourage interpretation and discussion of human behavior and values.

Third, literary texts enhance linguistic competence by providing rich vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and complex grammatical structures. Unlike simplified teaching materials, literature challenges students to deal with ambiguity, infer meaning, and interpret figurative language. This not only improves language proficiency but also trains critical and analytical skills essential for intercultural communication.

Finally, literature promotes learner motivation and personal engagement. Because literary texts often address universal human themes such as love, conflict, morality, and identity, they resonate with students on a personal level, making the learning process more meaningful. Teachers who integrate literature into EFL curricula often report higher levels of student participation and curiosity.

Thus, the results indicate that literature bridges the gap between linguistic competence and cultural competence, preparing learners for more effective and nuanced communication in international contexts.

Conclusion. Literary texts play a crucial role in teaching cultural competence in EFL classrooms. They expose learners to authentic cultural content, foster empathy, enhance linguistic skills, and stimulate personal engagement. While textbooks and functional materials are indispensable for structured learning, literature provides the cultural depth and interpretative challenges that truly prepare students for intercultural communication. Future studies should investigate how digital adaptations of literary texts – such as audiobooks, interactive reading platforms, and multimedia storytelling – can further support the development of cultural competence in online and blended learning environments.

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MYSTERY AND SUSPENSE IN GOTHIC LITERATURE: THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE WORKS OF POE AND DOSTOEVSKY

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Abstract: This paper explores the role of mystery and suspense in Gothic literature by analyzing Edgar Allan Poe's short story *The Tell-Tale Heart*. The study investigates how Poe uses elements of psychological horror and suspense to illustrate the protagonist's internal conflict, focusing on the symbolic representation of guilt through the motif of sound. The main question this research addresses is how mystery and suspense are used to develop the theme of guilt in the narrative. By examining the protagonist's psychological breakdown, this

paper reveals how Poe's mastery of suspense and symbolism deepens the horror and creates a chilling atmosphere. Furthermore, the study compares Poe's work with Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment* to show how both authors address themes of guilt and madness, albeit through different narrative techniques and psychological depth. The findings highlight the significance of Gothic literature in shaping modern psychological fiction. This paper contributes to a broader understanding of how Gothic elements-particularly suspense and psychological tension-are used to explore human emotions and moral dilemmas.

Key words: mystery, suspense, symbolism of sound, unreliable narrators, psychological tension, philosophical, the moral consequences

Introduction: Gothic literature is known for its dark, mysterious, and suspense-filled atmosphere. One of the most influential writers in this genre is Edgar Allan Poe, whose works delve deep into the human psyche, exploring themes of guilt, fear, and madness. His short story *The Tell-Tale Heart* stands out as a prime example of how mystery and suspense can be woven together to create a chilling narrative that reflects the protagonist's internal breakdown.

In this paper, I aim to explore how Poe uses the elements of mystery and suspense in *The Tell-Tale Heart* to reflect the protagonist's psychological unraveling. The key focus is on how Poe uses symbols - particularly sound, such as the heartbeat - to represent the protagonist's guilt and descent into madness. The story's structure, its unreliable narrator, and the buildup of suspense create an intense emotional experience for the reader, drawing them into the character's tortured mind.

The research question that drives this study is: How does Edgar Allan Poe use mystery, suspense, and symbolism to depict the psychological breakdown of his protagonist in *The Tell-Tale Heart*? This question is significant because it allows us to understand the ways in which Poe's writing contributes to the development of Gothic literature and psychological fiction. By analyzing the use of suspense in the story, we can see how it heightens the sense of fear and guilt in the narrative.

In addition to analyzing Poe's work, I will compare *The Tell-Tale Heart* with Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment*, another classic that explores themes of guilt and psychological conflict. Both authors share an interest in the complexities of the human mind, yet they approach these themes in different ways. While Poe's focus is on immediate emotional responses to guilt, Dostoevsky's portrayal of psychological breakdown is more gradual and philosophical. This comparison will help shed light on the different narrative techniques each author uses to explore similar themes.

Literature Review: Edgar Allan Poe's *The Tell-Tale Heart* has been widely studied for its use of psychological tension and its exploration of guilt. Several scholars have discussed how Poe uses mystery and suspense to portray the protagonist's mental disintegration. Abadli [2014] argues that the use of the unreliable narrator in Poe's story creates a deep sense of mystery, as the protagonist's disturbed perception of reality invites the reader to question what is true and what is a product of his madness. Hongkun [2015] discusses how the Gothic style in Poe's works evokes an atmosphere of dread and paranoia, which intensifies as the protagonist becomes more consumed by his guilt. This sense of growing suspense, according to Hongkun, mirrors the psychological unraveling that the character undergoes throughout the story. One of the key elements of *The Tell-Tale Heart* is the symbol of sound, particularly the heartbeat. Sun [2015] analyzes the role of sound in the story, pointing out that the heartbeat becomes a physical manifestation of the protagonist's inner turmoil. The heartbeat grows louder and more persistent as the protagonist's guilt intensifies, symbolizing his psychological collapse. This symbolic use of sound enhances the suspense, as the reader can feel the character's mounting panic and sense of impending doom.

The theme of madness and guilt is also central to Poe's story. Pezer [2020] discusses how Poe's exploration of madness in *The Tell-Tale Heart* transcends a simple narrative of horror. The protagonist's madness is intricately tied to his moral deterioration, and this connection between psychological collapse and guilt is a hallmark of Poe's work. Similarly, Amir [2020] emphasizes that the protagonist's inability to escape his own mind creates a claustrophobic atmosphere, where the reader is drawn into his spiraling thoughts. While Poe's *The Tell-Tale Heart* focuses on the immediate psychological effects of guilt, Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment* takes a more philosophical approach to the theme. Indrusiak [4,39-58-p] argues that in *Crime and Punishment*, Dostoevsky explores the existential weight of guilt, showing how it evolves gradually in Raskolnikov's mind. Unlike Poe's immediate psychological tension, Dostoevsky's narrative focuses on the long-term consequences of moral conflict and the gradual unraveling of the protagonist's psyche. Jandaghi and Zohdi [5,314-319-p] suggest that Dostoevsky uses symbols like dreams and visions to represent Raskolnikov's guilty conscience, which, unlike Poe's auditory symbols, is represented through a more abstract and introspective lens. This research builds on the existing literature by comparing how both authors explore the themes of guilt and psychological breakdown, focusing on their use of suspense and symbolism to convey these complex emotions. While Poe's focus is on the immediate emotional collapse of the protagonist, Dostoevsky's narrative emphasizes the gradual nature of moral deterioration. Both authors, however, demonstrate the power of suspense to reflect the inner turmoil of their characters.

Methods: This study uses a comparative qualitative approach to analyze two key literary works: Edgar Allan Poe's *The Tell-Tale Heart* and Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment*. The research focuses on key themes of guilt, conscience, and psychological breakdown in both stories. Through a detailed literary analysis, the study explores how the authors use suspense, symbols, and narrative techniques to portray these psychological elements. The analysis begins with a close reading of *The Tell-Tale Heart*, focusing on the use of sound (specifically the heartbeat) as a symbol of the protagonist's guilt. The first-person narrative allows for an immersive exploration of the protagonist's deteriorating mental state, with a particular emphasis on how Poe builds suspense throughout the story. The use of auditory imagery and repetition is key in creating an atmosphere of increasing tension. Next, *Crime and Punishment* is analyzed through a focus on the gradual evolution of Raskolnikov's guilt. The third-person perspective in Dostoevsky's novel provides insight into the character's inner conflict, which is represented through dreams and hallucinations. The study examines how Dostoevsky uses these symbols to reflect the psychological and philosophical dimensions of guilt. The comparative analysis of both texts highlights the differences in narrative structure, symbolism, and character development. Secondary sources are consulted to contextualize the findings and to compare the themes of guilt and psychological conflict in the works of Poe and Dostoevsky. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of how each author uses suspense and psychological depth to explore human emotions and moral dilemmas.

Results: In comparing *The Tell-Tale Heart* and *Crime and Punishment*, several key differences and similarities emerge in how the two authors explore themes of guilt and psychological breakdown. In Poe's story, the protagonist's guilt is represented through the symbolism of sound, particularly the heartbeat, which grows louder as the protagonist's mental state deteriorates. The heartbeat serves as a constant reminder of his crime, heightening the tension and building suspense. Poe's first-person narration allows readers to experience the protagonist's paranoia and guilt directly, making the psychological tension immediate and intense. On the other hand, Dostoevsky's portrayal of guilt in *Crime and*

Punishment is more gradual and philosophical. The symbolism of dreams and hallucinations represents Raskolnikov's psychological turmoil, reflecting the slow unraveling of his conscience. Unlike Poe's immediate depiction of guilt, Dostoevsky's narrative structure allows for a more reflective exploration of moral and existential questions. The third-person perspective offers a broader view of Raskolnikov's internal conflict, making the psychological breakdown more complex and introspective. Both authors use unreliable narrators to create suspense, but the narrative techniques differ. Poe's use of a first-person narrator draws the reader into the character's distorted perception of reality, while Dostoevsky's third-person narration allows for a broader exploration of the psychological and philosophical implications of guilt. Both works, however, use suspense as a tool to heighten the tension and to reflect the moral struggles of their protagonists.

Discussion: The comparison between Poe's *The Tell-Tale Heart* and Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment* reveals significant differences in how the two authors approach the theme of guilt and psychological breakdown. Poe's use of the heartbeat as a symbol of guilt is a powerful tool for creating suspense. The heartbeat, a direct and physical manifestation of guilt, serves as a constant reminder of the crime, pushing the protagonist to the brink of madness. Poe's first-person narrative ensures that the reader experiences the protagonist's growing paranoia and fear as the story progresses.

Dostoevsky, by contrast, offers a more gradual exploration of guilt. Raskolnikov's guilt is not symbolized by sound but rather through his increasingly erratic thoughts and dreams. Dostoevsky focuses on the long-term psychological effects of guilt, illustrating how it gnaws away at the protagonist's conscience over time. The slow, almost unbearable, mental unraveling is presented through a third-person perspective, giving the reader more insight into the character's internal struggles and moral dilemmas.

Both authors, however, are concerned with the psychological impact of guilt and the moral consequences of their protagonists' actions. Poe creates immediate tension and horror through his use of sound, while Dostoevsky's gradual development of guilt allows for a deeper philosophical exploration of human nature. In both works, suspense serves to highlight the psychological tension of the characters and their inevitable collapse.

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LINGVOPOETIK IFODA VOSITALAR VA ULARNING GYOTE ASARLARIDAGI BADIY FUNKSIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Gyotening badiiy asarlaridagi lingvopoetik ifoda vositalari - metafora, epitet, o'xshatish, parallelizm va antitezalar - tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda R. Jakobson, Yu. Lotman, V. Vinogradov, M. Riffaterre va P. Ricœurning lingvopoetika haqidagi nazariy qarashlariga tayanilgan. Gyote asarlarida inson ruhiyati, tabiat va estetik tafakkur uyg'unligi lingvopoetik nuqtayi nazardan tahlil etilib, til vositalarining estetik vazifasi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvopoetika, badiiy obraz, estetik ta'sir, metafora, parallelizm, poetik til, Gyote, Werther, Faust, ruhiy kechinma.

Lingvopoetika - bu tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslik tutashgan soha bo'lib, badiiy matnning til vositalari orqali estetik ta'sir yaratish usullarini o'rganadi. Lingvopoetika so'zning oddiy kommunikativ vazifasidan tashqari, uning badiiy-estetik imkoniyatini, hissiy energiyasini va semantik chuqurligini tahlil qiladi. Lingvopoetika tahlil markaziga badiiy tilni, ya'ni yozuvchi yoki shoirning individual uslubini qo'yadi. Boshqacha aytganda, bu yo'nalish badiiy asarda so'zning qanday shaklda, ohangda, ritmda va sintaktik tuzilishda qo'llanib, qanday badiiy ta'sir hosil qilganini o'rganadi.

Lingvopoetika atamasi XX asr tilshunosligida shakllanib, badiiy matnning til vositalari orqali estetik ta'sir yaratish mexanizmlarini o'rganadigan ilmiy yo'nalish sifatida qaror topgan. Ushbu yo'nalishning shakllanishi, avvalo, rus va g'arb tilshunoslik maktablarida ilgari surilgan poetik nazariyalar bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Lingvopoetika tushunchasini ilmiy muomalaga birinchi bo'lib rus-amerikalik tilshunos R. Jakobson kiritgan. U o'zining "Linguistics and Poetics" nomli asarida tilning olti asosiy funksiyasidan biri sifatida poetik funksiyani ajratadi. Jakobsonning fikricha, poetik funksiya xabarning mazmuniga emas, balki uning ifoda shakliga, ya'ni so'zning ohangi, ritmi, tovush uyg'unligi va sintaktik tuzilishiga e'tibor qaratadi [1]. [1,87-b] Shu tarzda olim tilning estetik mohiyatini tahlil qilish zaruratini ilmiy asosda ilgari surdi va lingvopoetika uchun nazariy poydevor yaratdi.

Jakobson g'oyalarini davom ettirgan Yu. Lotman lingvopoetikani semiotik tizim sifatida talqin etib, badiiy matnni shunchaki axborot uzatuvchi emas, balki yangi ma'no yaratuvchi tizim deb hisoblaydi. Uning fikricha, har bir badiiy asar o'zining ichki tuzilishi, ritmi va so'zlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar orqali estetik ma'no hosil qiladi. Shu bois lingvopoetik tahlil matnning sathdagi ma'nosidan tashqari, uning yashirin semantik qatlamlarini ochishga qaratiladi [2]. [2,54-b] M. Riffaterre lingvopoetikani poetik semantika nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil qilib, badiiy matnni o'quvchini so'zning bevosita ma'nosidan yashirin semantik qatlamlarga olib kiruvchi estetik tizim sifatida baholaydi. [3, 91-b.] P. Ricœur esa lingvopoetikani til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi estetik ko'priksifatida izohlaydi hamda metaforani inson tafakkurining yaratuvchan kuchi deb talqin etadi [4, 132-b.].

Rus tilshunosligi vakili V. Vinogradov o'zining "О языке художественной литературы" asarida badiiy nutqni til tizimining alohida estetik shakli sifatida talqin qiladi. U lingvopoetikani adabiy uslubshunoslik bilan bevosita bog'lab, poetik tilni "so'zning badiiy obrazga aylangan shakli" sifatida ta'riflaydi [5, 63-b.]. O'zbek adabiyotshunosligida esa N. Jo'raqulov va G'. Yoqubovlarning asarlarida lingvopoetik tahlil matnning semantik, fonetik va ritmik xususiyatlarini qamrab oluvchi ilmiy yondashuv sifatida izohlanadi [6, 7].

Yuqoridagi olimlar qarashlaridan kelib chiqadiki, lingvopoetika - bu tilning badiiy funksiyasini, ya'ni so'z orqali estetik ta'sir yaratish qonuniyatlarini o'rganadigan kompleks ilmiy yo'nalishdir. U badiiy asar tili orqali muallifning estetik dunyoqarashi, milliy tafakkuri va individual uslubini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Shunday qilib, lingvopoetika badiiy so'z san'atining ilmiy talqini bo'lib, so'z, ma'no va hissiyotning uyg'unlashuvi orqali go'zallik yaratish jarayonini tahlil qiladi.

Gyote ijodida lingvopoetik vositalar shaxsiy kechinmalar, tabiat manzaralari va falsafiy mushohadalar orqali ifoda topgan. Uning asarlarida soʻz oddiy aloqa vositasi emas, balki badiiy-estetik mazmun yaratuvchi hodisa sifatida namoyon boʻladi. Maqolaning maqsadi - Gyote asarlarida qoʻllangan lingvopoetik vositalarning badiiy funksiyasini tahlil qilishdir.

Gyote lingvopoetik mahorati shundaki, u soʻzning tashqi shakli bilan ichki maʼnosi oʻrtasida mukammal uygʻunlik yaratadi. Uning har bir badiiy ifodasi orqasida inson ruhining ichki harorati, hayot falsafasi va estetik qarashlari mujassam. Muallifning tili nafaqat voqeani tasvirlaydi, balki uni his ettiradi, oʻquvchini bevosita ruhiy kechinmaga olib kiradi. Shu bois Gyote asarlari lingvopoetika nuqtayi nazaridan soʻz, ohang va obraz uchligi asosida qurilgan estetik tizim sifatida qaraladi.

“Faust” asarida muallif metafora va antitezalardan keng foydalanib, ezgulik va yovuzlik, nur va zulmat, ruh va tana oʻrtasidagi abadiy kurashni badiiy shaklda ifodalaydi. Masalan, “Nur ichidan zulmatga, zulmatdan nurga qaytish” gʻoyasi insonning ichki oʻzgarishi, ruhiy yuksalish jarayonining ramziga aylanadi. Bu yerdagi lingvopoetik vositalar - metafora, ramz va sintaktik parallelizm - matnga falsafiy chuqurlik va musiqiy ohang bagʻishlaydi.

“Yosh Verterning iztiroblari”da esa Gyote romantik ruhiyatni epitet, oʻxshatish, takror va inversiya orqali ochadi. Verterning har bir maktubida til poetik tuygʻuga aylanadi: tabiat manzaralari qahramon ruhiyatining inʼikosi sifatida tasvirlanadi. Yomgʻir, daryo, quyosh va togʻ obrazlari orqali muallif tabiatni ruhning badiiy metaforasiga aylantiradi. Bu esa Gyote tilidagi lingvopoetik obrazlarning psixologik funksiyasini koʻrsatadi va ular hissiy holatni tildagi badiiy shaklga aylantiradi.

Gyotening lingvopoetik uslubi uning falsafiy tafakkuri, psixologik teranligi va estetik didini yuksak darajada aks ettiradi. Yozuvchi asarlarida badiiy obrazlar inson va tabiat, ruh va materiya, muhabbat va iztirob, nur va zulmat singari qarama-qarshi tushunchalarning uygʻunligidan tugʻiladi. Shu bois uning poetik tili lingvopoetik nuqtayi nazardan inson ruhiyatining estetik modeli sifatida qaraladi.

Bu fikrga “Yosh Verterning iztiroblari” romanidagi quyidagi parcha yorqin dalil boʻla oladi. Asarda yozuvchi tabiat manzaralari orqali qahramon ruhiyatining oʻzgaruvchan holatini badiiy tilda ifodalaydi:

Oʻzbekcha: *Mana endi yomgʻir sharros quyib, goh boʻron quturib, yer goh muzlab, goh erib yotganda, koʻchadan koʻra uyda oʻtirish yaxshiroq-ku, axir, deb oʻylayman-da, yengil tortib ketaman. Agar ertalab quyosh charaqlab, ochiq kundan darak bersa, mana, odamlar bir-birlaridan qizgʻanadigan tagʻin bir xudo marhamati! - deb xitob qilishdan oʻzimni tiyolmayman. ! [8 fevra]*

Nemischa: *Wenn's nun recht regnet und stöbert und fröstelt und taut: ha! Denk' ich, kann's doch zu Hause nicht schlimmer werden, als es draußen ist, oder umgekehrt, und so ist's gut. Geht die Sonne des Morgens auf und verspricht einen feinen Tag, erwehr' ich mir niemals auszurufen: da haben sie doch wieder ein himmlisches Gut, worum sie einander bringen können! [8 Februar]*

Bu satrlarda yozuvchi ob-havo holatini tasvirlar ekan, u orqali Verterning ichki kechinmalarini ifodalaydi. Yomgʻir, boʻron, muzlash va erish kabi tabiat hodisalari ruhiy beqarorlik, oʻzgaruvchan kayfiyat ramziga aylanadi, quyoshning charaqlashi esa umid, iliqlik va ruhiy yengillikni bildiradi. Tashqi manzara orqali ichki kechinmaning ifodalanishi Gyote poetikasiga xos tabiat–ruhiyat parallelizmini yaratadi.

Nemischa matnda feʼllarning ketma-ketligi (*regnet – stöbert – fröstelt – taut*) ritmik gradatsiya hosil qilib, tabiatning harakat dinamikasini kuchaytiradi. Shu tarzda ritm va tovush

uyg'unligi o'quvchiga shunchaki manzara emas, balki ruhiy tebranishni his etish imkonini beradi. O'zbek tarjimasida esa "yomg'ir sharros quyib, goh bo'ron quturib" shaklida dinamik ifoda yanada tabiiy ohangda berilgan bo'lib, bu pragmatik ekvivalentlikni ta'minlaydi. Bundan tashqari, "xudo marhamati" birikmasi asliyatdagi *ein himmlisches Gut* ifodasining milliy-madaniy moslashtirilgan ko'rinishidir. Bu o'rinda tarjimon domestikatsiya usulidan foydalangan holda o'zbek o'quvchisi uchun tushunarli va tabiiy obraz yaratgan. Shuningdek, parchaning umumiy ohangida antitezalar tashqaridagi bo'ron va uydagi osoyishtalik, yomg'ir va quyosh, sovuq va ilqlik o'zaro qarama-qarshi, lekin uyg'un badiiy tizimni tashkil etadi.

Shunday qilib, bu epizodda Gyote tabiat tasvirini ruhiy kechinma bilan birlashtirgan holda lingvopoetik birlik yaratadi. Tabiatdagi o'zgarishlar qahramon kayfiyatining aksadosiga aylanadi, ritm, metafora, o'xshatish va antitezalar esa asarga musiqiy ohang va estetik chuqurlik baxsh etadi. Shu jihatdan, "Yosh Verterning iztiroblari" romanining ushbu parchasini yozuvchining lingvopoetik mahoratini, ya'ni inson ruhiyatini badiiy til orqali ifodalash san'atini namoyon etuvchi yorqin namunasi deb baholash mumkin.

Gyote poetikasida inson ruhiyati va tabiat o'rtasidagi uyg'unlik alohida o'rin tutadi. Yozuvchi tabiat manzaralari orqali inson ichki dunyosining o'zgaruvchan holatini, ruhiy tebranishlarini badiiy tilda ifodalaydi. "Yosh Verterning iztiroblari" romanidagi quyidagi parcha bu fikrni aniq tasdiqlaydi: **O'zbekcha:** "*Tabiat kuzga bo'yin ega boshlaganidanoq, mening yuragimda va atrofimda ham hazinlik boshlanadi.*" [4 sentabr] **Nemischa:** *Wie die Natur sich zum Herbste neigt, wird es Herbst in mir und um mich her.* [4 September].

Nemischa matnda "*Herbst in mir und um mich her*" iborasi ikki qatlamli ma'noga ega: "menda kuz" - ichki ruhiy holat, "atrofimda kuz" - tashqi manzara. Ushbu parallel tuzilma muallif uslubidagi uyg'unlikni kuchaytiradi. Shu bilan birga, "Herbst" so'zining ikki bor takrorlanishi matnga ritmik barqarorlik beradi va ruhiy kechinmani tovush orqali his etish imkonini yaratadi.

O'zbek tarjimasida "*Tabiat kuzga bo'yin ega boshlaganidanoq*" jumlasida asliyatdagi *sich zum Herbste neigt* ifodasining semantik nozikligini to'liq saqlaydi. "*Bo'yin egmoq*" ifodasi kuzning boshlanishini jonlantirib, tabiatni go'yo inson singari his qiluvchi mavjudot sifatida tasvirlaydi. Bu yerda personifikatsiya vositasi orqali tabiat ruhiylashtiriladi, natijada tabiat va inson o'rtasida badiiy bog'liqlik vujudga keladi.

"*Yuragimda va atrofimda ham hazinlik boshlanadi*" degan qism esa parallelizm va takror orqali ichki va tashqi olam o'rtasidagi uyg'unlikni yanada kuchaytiradi. Ruhiy holat va tabiat manzarasi o'zaro tayanadi, bir-birini to'ldiradi. Shu jihatdan, Gyotening bu ifodasi inson ruhiy holatining badiiy modelini yaratadi - kuz faqat tabiatdagi mavsumiy o'zgarish emas, balki qalbdagi tinchlik, iztirob va sokin tushkunlikning metaforasidir.

Shunday qilib, ushbu parcha Gyote lingvopoetik uslubining muhim xususiyatini - inson ruhiyati va tabiat go'zalligining estetik uyg'unligini yaqqol namoyon etadi. Yozuvchi til vositalari - metafora, personifikatsiya, parallelizm va ritmik takrorlar orqali insonning ruhiy kechinmalarini tabiat manzarasi bilan bir butun tarzda tasvirlaydi. Lingvopoetika tilning badiiy funksiyasini, ya'ni so'z orqali estetik ta'sir yaratish qonuniyatlarini o'rganadigan kompleks ilmiy yo'nalishdir. U badiiy asar tili orqali muallifning estetik dunyoqarashi, milliy tafakkuri va individual uslubini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

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FOUNDERS OF THE EASTERN RENAISSANCE

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Abstract: This article scientifically analyzes and reveals the role of the founders of the Eastern Renaissance and their rare works today, as well as their exemplary aspects for the younger generation.

Keywords: Mawarannahr, Islam, religion, great scholars, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Imam Bukhari, Al-Khwarizmi, Renaissance.

Mawarannahr was one of the centers of Islamic culture and scientific development in the Middle Ages. Great scholars from this region achieved tremendous success in science, philosophy, art, and religion. Their works influenced not only the Muslim world but also European science. The development of Islamic culture in Mawarannahr and the impact of Islam on the cultural environment was profound and comprehensive, continuing over centuries. Islam entered this region through the Arab Caliphate in the 7th century, and by the beginning of the 8th century, it began to spread widely among most of the population. The influence of Islam on life was reflected in the following:

Development of science and culture: With the spread of Islam, scientific and cultural life in Mawarannahr flourished. Major scientific centers emerged in cities like Bukhara, Samarkand, and Khorezm. Great scientists such as Al-Farghani, Beruni, and Ibn Sina became globally famous by applying Islamic principles to science.

Sufism - is a teaching that combines religious and secular views, which has enriched our people's spirituality and shaped their social thinking based on noble ideas over many centuries. Its influence on the development of the region's art, culture, literature, and philosophical sciences is incomparable[1:1-3].

Architectural heritage: The influence of Islamic culture was also clearly manifested in architecture. Mosques, madrasas, mausoleums, and shrines became an integral part of Mawarannahr architecture. Examples include the Shakhi-Zinda complex in Samarkand and the Poi Kalon Mosque in Bukhara.

Social life: Islam had a great impact on the daily lifestyle of the local population. It introduced new principles in ethics, family life, education, and trade. At the same time, certain aspects of local cultural traditions were integrated with Islam.

Today, the scientific legacy of these scholars continues to be studied by scientists worldwide. In particular, Imam Bukhari compiled several works of high scientific importance: "Al-jami as-sahih," "Al-adab al-mufrad," "At-tarikh al-kabir," and others. From this information, we can clearly be convinced that Imam Bukhari left an indelible mark in Muslim history. For example, his work "Al-jami as-sahih" is considered second only to the Quran among the books of believers, because it reliably presents authentic and non-authentic hadiths. Thanks to Imam Bukhari, numerous schools of hadith studies were established and successfully operated in Mawarannahr during the 9th-12th centuries. Today, the works of our

great ancestors have been translated into dozens of languages worldwide, and his contributions are utilized in numerous studies in the Islamic world[2].

Al-Khwarizmi - the great mathematician, astronomer, and geographer Abu Ja'far Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi was born in 783 in Khiva. He gained a high reputation in history as the founder of algebra. We know well that the word "algebra" itself comes from his treatise "Al-jabr wal-muqabala." His treatise on arithmetic was based on Hindu numerals and led to the spread of the decimal counting system and operations that we use today in Europe. Indeed, in today's globalized world, it is not difficult to see that in some developed countries in Europe and other continents, there are views of Islam as a backward religion based on terrorism that only harms people. However, they do not even imagine that the scientists who were the main contributors to their present development were adherents of Islam. In particular, without Al-Khwarizmi's foundation of algorithms, it would be difficult to imagine the emergence of all our mobile devices, including our phones and computers that have become an essential part of our ordinary lives, as well as the developing artificial intelligence of today[3:56-60].

Abu Rayhan Beruni was born in 973 in the ancient city of Kyot. He mastered all the sciences of his time, primarily astronomy, physics, mathematics, theology, and mineralogy. Beruni created more than 150 works. His works such as "Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples," "India," and "Geodesy" are among them. It should also be emphasized that Beruni knew Islam well. Additionally, Abu Rayhan Beruni's correspondence with Ibn Sina took place during his time in Gurganj. Only 18 of their questions, answers, and criticisms have reached us. This correspondence shows that he was also interested in issues of natural philosophy and physics. In these exchanges, the two famous scientists conducted scientific discussions on issues such as space, heat propagation, thermal expansion of bodies, reflection, and refraction of light[4].

Abu Ali Ibn Sina (real name Abu Ali al-Husayn Ibn Abdullah Ibn al-Husayn Ibn Ali) was born in 980 in the village of Afshona. The scientist who made a huge contribution to the development of world science was called "Sheikh ar-Rais" (leader of the wise men), "Sharaf al-mulk" (honor and prestige of the country), "Hakim al-wazir" (wise man of the vizier) in the East, while in the West he is famous as Avicenna. Ibn Sina's work "Al-qanun fit-tib" (Canon of Medicine) was translated into Latin in the 12th century and was used as the main medical manual in Europe until the 17th century. Although the work that made him famous in the West as "Avicenna" was "The Canon of Medicine," the title "Sheikh ar-Rais" indicates his greatness as a philosopher, so we can hardly doubt that Ibn Sina had perfect knowledge not only of medicine but also philosophy. In the history of world science, Ibn Sina is recognized as an encyclopedic scientist because he dealt with all existing sciences of his time and wrote works on them. Returning to "The Canon of Medicine," it covers many important medical issues such as the causes and sources of diseases, diagnosis, treatment methods, properties of medicinal plants and medicines, diet, and the importance of physical exercise for human health.

From the above, we can conclude that all these scholars had high capabilities, and most importantly, they all were believers of Islam and had perfect knowledge of religion. Unfortunately, negative attitudes toward religion are increasing today. For example, all the great thinkers memorized the Quran from childhood and became Qaris (Quran reciters), but today, the age limit for studying religion is set at 16 years. In our opinion, it is important to introduce the younger generation to both secular and religious knowledge. This is because Islam is based on ethics, and this religion has always operated according to the principles of interfaith tolerance. In Islam, which is being portrayed today as the cause of conflicts, scholars

of other faiths were also encouraged and not hindered in their work. As an example, Caliph Mamun gathered scholars of various religions and sects in the "Mamun Academy" and said, "Debate whatever you want from knowledge, just don't cite from your religious books so that sectarian problems don't arise"[5:101]. From this, we can conclude that it's not us but they who are seeking conflict.

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AMIR TEMUR ROMANIDA ANTOROPONIMLARNING QO‘LLANISH XUSUSIYATI (B.Axmedov asari asosida)

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek adabiy tilida antroponimlarning, ya’ni kishi ismlarining shakllanishi va ularning tarixiy hamda madaniy ma’nosi haqida so‘z yuritiladi. Bo‘riboy Ahmedovning “Amir Temur” romanidagi shaxs nomlari tahlil qilinib, ularning tuzilishi va mazmuni o‘rganilgan. Asardagi “bek”, “xon”, “xo‘ja”, “amir” kabi so‘zlar ismlarga qanday qo‘shilgani va ular orqali o‘sha davr jamiyatidagi ijtimoiy farqlar ifodalangani ko‘rsatib berilgan. Maqola o‘zbek antroponimikasi bo‘yicha ilmiy ma’lumotlarni boyitishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar. O‘zbek adabiy tili, antroponimika, onomastika, Bo‘riboy Ahmedov, “Amir Temur” romani, shaxs nomlari, tarixiy shaxslar, lingvistik tahlil, ijtimoiy-ma’naviy mazmun, nom berish an’analari.

Abstract: This article discusses the formation of anthroponyms, i.e., personal names, in the Uzbek literary language, as well as their historical and cultural significance. The study analyzes the personal names found in Bo‘riboy Ahmedov’s novel “*Amir Temur*”, examining their structure and meaning. It is shown how words such as “*bek*”, “*khan*”, “*khoja*”, and “*amir*” were added to names and how they reflected social distinctions in the society of that time. The article contributes to enriching scientific knowledge in the field of Uzbek anthroponymy.

Key words: Uzbek literary language, anthroponymy, onomastics, Bo‘riboy Ahmedov, “*Amir Temur*” novel, personal names, historical figures, linguistic analysis, socio-cultural meaning, naming traditions.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается формирование антропонимов, то есть личных имён, в узбекском литературном языке, а также их историческое и культурное значение. Проанализированы имена персонажей в романе Бўрибой

Ахмедова «Амира Темура», изучены их структура и смысл. Показано, как такие слова, как «бек», «хан», «хожа», «амир», присоединялись к именам и отражали социальные различия в обществе того времени. Статья способствует обогащению научных знаний в области узбекской антропонимики.

Ключевые слова: узбекский литературный язык, антропонимика, ономастика, Бўрибой Ахмедов, роман «Амир Темура», имена персонажей, исторические личности, лингвистический анализ, социально-культурное содержание, традиции именования.

Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili asrlar davomida qo'llanib kelingan yagona o'zbek tili taraqqiyotining yuqori shakli milliy tilning ishlanganligidir.

Antroponimika – onamastikaning kishi ismlari, ularning kelib chiqishi, tarqalishi kabi masalalarni o'rganadi. [1, 41b.]

Kishilik jamiyati paydo bo'libdiki, insonlar o'zlarini boshqalardan ajralib turishlari uchun turli nomlardan foydalanib keladilar. Qadimda nom insonga u tug'ilgan paytga emas, balki ulg'ayib, voyaga yetganidan so'ng uning jismoniy yoki aqliy rivojlanishiga qarab berilgan.

Antroponimika XX asrning 60-yillaridan turkiyshunoslikda, jumladan, o'zbek tilshunosligida toponimika bilan bir qatorda alohida ilmiy yo'naliy sifatida shakllana boshladi. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham o'zbek anomastikasi va antroponimikasiga oid til birliklarini, ya'ni bu soha terminologiyasini to'plash, tartibga solish va lingvistik jihatdan o'rganishda, anomastika va antroponimikaga oid ilmiy terminlardagi xilma-xillik nuqsonlarni bartaraf etish borasida E.Begmatovning monografik tadqiqotlari [2,263b.] anomastikaga, xususan, antroponimikaga tamal toshini qo'ydi.

Demak yuqoridagi fikrlardan kelib chiqib, tildagi atoqli otlarni anglatuvchi, diqqatimizni tortgan lingvistik hodisalar o'rtasidagi munosabatni yoritishga harakat qildik.

Ushbu maqolamizda Bo'riboy Ahmedovning "Amir Temur" romanidagi qo'llangan shaxs arxisemali leksemalarning ma'lum bir narsa, predmeti anglatishga ko'ra, mazmuniy guruhlariga ajratib, ularni umumiy va xususiy guruhlariga, birlashtiruvchi va farqlovchi tomonlarini tahlil qilishni o'z oldimizga maqsad qilib oldik.

"Amir Temur" romanidagi tarixiy personajlar ismlarini diqqat bilan tahlil qilar ekanmiz, ularda ijtimoiy davrdagi tabaqalanish, hokimiyatga talashish ismlarga joy nomlarining va urug' nomlarining qo'shilishi o'zaro munosabatlar ko'rinib turadi.

Asarda qo'llangan antroponimlarni tarkibiy jihatdan quyidagi guruhlariga ajratdik:

1.Tarixiy shaxslarni bildiruvchi antroponimlar: Amir Temur, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy, Ilyosxo'jaxon, Tug'luq Temirxon, Tarag'ay Bahodir.

Shunchaki o'zim, xon hazrat, – Temurbek javob uchun boshqa so'z topolmadi. (B.Ahmedov. Amir Temur. 376). *Ilyosxo'ja Temurbekni imtihon qilishda davom etdi.* (B.Ahmedov. Amir Temur. 37-b). *Buni amir Hojibek ham, Tug'luq Temirxon yaxshi bilishadi.* (Amir Temur. 30-b). *Bu yozuvlikni, muarrix Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiyning so'zlariga qaraganda, bir to'da buzuqi odamlar qilishgan ekan.* (Amir Temur. 51-bet). – *Fikri ojizimcha, ushbu mansabga Tarag'oy Bahodirning farzandi arjumandi Temurbek manosib.* (Amir Temur. 107-bet).

2.Antroponimlarga urug' nomlarini qo'shish: Hoji barlos, Boyazid jaloyir, Zoku barlos, Sulaymon barlos, Jaloliddin barlos, Hunduka barlos.

-Amakingiz Hoji barlos janoblari yubordilar bizni (Amir Temur. 16-bet). – *Haq gapni aytdingiz, janobi amir, to'g'ri maslahat, - qo'shildi unga Boyazid jaloyir* (Amir temur. 34-bet). – *Nima, nima bo'ldi, o'zi?* – *Joki barlos cho'chib ko'zlarini ochdi.* (Amir Temur. 43-bet). *Shundan keyin Temurbek uch yuz sara yigitni – ularning orasida nomdor beklardan*

Sulaymon barlos, Bahrom jaloyir va Jaloliddin barloslar ham bor edi –o‘zi bilan birga olib, Kesh sari yuzlandi. (Amir Temur. 96-bet).

3. Birinchi kopponenti “Amir” so‘zi bilan ifodalangan antroponimlar:

Amir Kulol allomayi zamon Shahobiddin Suhravardiyning xalfasi bo‘lib, diniy ilmlar hamda tariqat sulhini puxta egallagan bilimdon odam edi. (Amir Temur. 18-bet). Amir Hojbek samimiyatligi va odam oxunligi bilan Temurbekda yaxshi taassurot qoldirdi. (Amir Temur. 26-bet). Yana anavi Qazaganning nabirasi amir Husayn ham bor. (Amir Temur. 29-bet).

4. Antroponimlarga “bek” komponentlarining qo‘shilib kelishi: - *Temurbek, muncha xayol surmasangiz. “O‘ychi – o‘yiga yetguncha, tavakkalchi uyiga yetibdur”, degan gap bor. (Amir Temur. 35-bet). – Joni molimiz sizning inon-ixtiyoringizda, -dedi hamma uchun amir Hojibek. (Amir Temur. 36-bet). –Hamma narsa xudodin, Husaynbek. Ajal yetmagan bo‘lsa, yetti kechayu-kunduz bo‘ron turg‘onda ham odamlar tirik qolg‘onlar. (Amir Temur. 62-bet).*

5. Antroponimlarga “joy” komponentlarini qo‘shib aytish: *O‘sha avom un-nos, Mavlonozoda, Abubakr Kaloviy, Xurdak Buxoriyga o‘xshaganlar uni mug‘ul istilosidin asrab qoldi. (Amir Temur. 119-bet). Andak xatolik bo‘libdur, bek, -dedi Kaffol Shoshiy mozorining shayxi xoja Boboxon (Amir Temur. 148-bet). Xon bilan amir Husayn shu yerda qolishdi, asosiy kuchlar Temurbek boshchiligida shoh Shayx Ali Badaxshoniyga qarshi o‘lkaning ichkarisiga yuborildi. (Amir Temur. 157-b).*

6. Antroponimlarga “xon” komponentining qo‘shilishi: *Asirlar orasida Ilyosxo‘jaxonning o‘zi ham bor edi. (Amir Temur. 100-b). – Janobi oliylari, xon ibn hoqon Durjixon ibn Ilchikdoy ibn Duvaxon ibn Chig‘atoyxon ibn sohibqironi a‘zam Chingizxon shu yerdalar. (Amir Temur. 109-b). U 1220-yili Chingizxon xuruji davrida vayron qilingandi. (Amir Temur. 113-b). Keyin bu xatni Durjixonga yetkazdilar, xon esa xatni Tormoshirining bevasi O‘rda xotinning qo‘liga tutqazdi. (Amir Temur. 126-b).*

7. Antroponimlarga “xo‘ja” komponentining qo‘shilishi: - *Biz, oching jiyan! – ovoz Nuridinxo‘jaga tanish tuyildi. (Amir Temur. 102-b). Shu payt Ilyosxo‘jaxon, “barongir qism chekinsin!” deb buyruq berdi. (Amir Temur. 112-b). Shu niyat bilan u yerga avval Temurxo‘ja o‘g‘lon, Jovurchi va Abbas bahodirni yetti qo‘shin qilib yubordi. (Amir Temur. 113-b). Amir Hindu aka bilan Dovudxo‘ja Keshdan kelgan amirlarni burnidan chiqquncha yedirib ichirdilar. (Amir Temur. 113-b).*

Xulosa qilib aytganda, tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, Onamastik nom berish “Amir temur” tarixiy romanda yuzlab antroponimlar qo‘llanganligini ko‘rsatadi. Bundan tashqari nom tushunchasi o‘sha davr jamiyatining turli davrlardagi madaniy jihatlari haqida muhim axborot yetkazuvchi kalit vazifasini ham o‘taydi.

Ismlarning ijtimoiy hodisa ekanligi, ismlarni tanlash motivida, shuningdek, ismlarning o‘ziga turli ijtimoiy, etnografik, diniy ma’nolar yuksalishida ham ko‘rinadi. Bundan tashqari, G.N.Gumilevning yozishicha, qadimiy davrda turklarning tug‘ilganda berilgan ismi shaxsning ijtimoiy ahvoli, jamiyatdagi o‘rniga qarab o‘zgarib turgan. [3,65b.]

Umuman olganda, ismlar jamiyatda yashaydi, jamiyat uchun yaratiladi. B.Ahmedovning “Amir Temur” tarixiy romandagi onamastika, antroponimasini o‘rganish yangi fakt va dalillar bilan to‘ldirishga xizmat qiladi.

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THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN IMPROVING STUDENTS’ PRODUCTIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. This article explores how literature (novels, short stories, drama, poetry) can contribute to the development of students’ productive skills, especially speaking and writing. It reviews theoretical rationales, empirical studies, and pedagogical strategies. The article argues that literature not only motivates learners but provides rich input, cultural context, vocabulary, models of discourse, and prompts for creative output. It also discusses challenges and offers practical recommendations for teachers.

Key words: literature, productive skills, speaking, writing, motivation, pedagogy, vocabulary, integration, language.

Productive skills in language learning – speaking and writing – are vital for learners to communicate, produce messages, and express ideas. Many language-teaching approaches have emphasized receptive skills (listening, reading), but without sufficient development of productive skills, learners remain passive receivers rather than active users of the language. In this light, literature offers a promising medium: it provides authentic language input, cultural richness, rich lexical and syntactic structures, and stimuli for learners to produce discourse themselves. This article aims to discuss the theoretical foundations, empirical evidence, and pedagogical strategies concerning the integration of literature into language classrooms to improve students’ productive skills. It also addresses challenges and offers suggestions for implementation.

Krashen’s Input Hypothesis and Swain’s Output Hypothesis provide a basis: learners need comprehensible input (which literature can supply) and opportunities to produce output to push their interlanguage forward. Literature can serve as “pushed input” that is just beyond learners’ current level, encouraging noticing of new forms. Moreover, producing written or spoken responses to literature fosters output, which can promote noticing, reformulation, and internalization.

Vygotskian sociocultural theory also supports using literature: learners engage in dialogic interaction (student–teacher, student–student) around texts, scaffolding each other’s productive output. Literature can serve as a mediation tool in the zone of proximal development.

Literary texts also offer rhetorical moves, discourse organization, stylistic devices, and cohesive devices. Exposure to these can help learners internalize discourse models and mimic them in their own production. [1]

Finally, from a motivation theory perspective, literature often engages learners emotionally and intellectually; this increased engagement can lead to more effort in productive tasks.

Empirical evidence on literature and productive skills. A number of empirical studies support the role of literature in improving writing and speaking. Abdalrahman found that integrating literary genres in English classrooms motivates learners to use both receptive and productive skills. [2] A study of using literature circles in small groups showed improvements in students’ language output and communicative confidence. [3]

Research on novel integration in undergraduate courses showed that students perceived novel teaching to benefit their writing of sentences and paragraphs. [4]

The study “The effect of writing practice on improving speaking skill” found that writing practice interventions also had positive effects on speaking proficiency.[4]

The study “The impact of speaking activities on writing skills in English as a foreign language (EFL)” provided evidence that speaking activities can lead to improved writing outcomes.[5]

The review “The benefits and challenges of integrating literary texts” [6] documents that literary works play a role in developing critical thinking, which supports richer spoken or written output.

Together, these studies show that literature can contribute to improved writing and speaking, via increased motivation, better models, rich language input, and prompts for output.

Literature plays a multifaceted role in developing productive skills through several interrelated mechanisms. Firstly, literary texts provide rich linguistic input that exposes learners to authentic and sophisticated language structures. When students engage with literary works, they encounter an abundance of varied vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, collocations, and discourse markers that are seldom found in conventional textbooks. This exposure allows them to internalize more natural language patterns and to use these structures effectively in their own writing and speaking. The rhythm, imagery, and figurative language of literature enrich the learner’s linguistic awareness, enhancing their expressive power and stylistic range.

Secondly, literature serves as a model of discourse and genre. Through narratives, descriptive passages, dialogues, and argumentative essays, students experience a wide array of communicative functions and rhetorical patterns. Analyzing the organization of ideas, the flow of arguments, and the interplay of characters helps learners understand how texts are structured and how meaning is constructed. This implicit learning process equips them with templates that they can adapt and reproduce when generating their own texts or spoken discourse.

Another essential mechanism is the stimulus for discussion and writing prompts that literature provides. The themes, conflicts, and characters within literary works provoke emotional and intellectual responses, leading students to articulate opinions, reflections, and analyses. In discussing literary texts, learners are encouraged to justify their ideas, make comparisons, and express interpretations, all of which foster spontaneous and meaningful language production. When tasked with writing about these topics, students draw upon their comprehension and creativity, producing language that is both contextually grounded and personally engaging.

Moreover, literature encourages critical thinking and creativity. Unlike factual texts, literary works often leave room for interpretation, inviting learners to infer meaning, question motives, and explore multiple perspectives. This interpretive process stimulates higher-order thinking and requires learners to express nuanced ideas in their own words, whether orally or in writing. Such reflective engagement not only strengthens linguistic output but also develops the ability to organize arguments logically and coherently.

Peer interaction and collaboration also play a vital role in this process. When students discuss literature in pairs or small groups, they negotiate meaning, share interpretations, and co-construct knowledge. This dialogic interaction enhances their communicative competence and helps them refine their language in real time. Literature thus becomes a platform for

meaningful communication, where learners can practice both speaking and listening in authentic, purposeful contexts.

Finally, literature creates opportunities for revision and reflection. As students compose written responses or creative pieces inspired by literary texts, they are encouraged to review and refine their drafts. The process of revising based on teacher or peer feedback promotes self-awareness and metacognitive growth. Through this iterative process, learners not only enhance grammatical accuracy but also develop a more sophisticated command of expression, style, and tone.

Teachers can effectively use literature to develop productive skills by integrating it into communicative and writing tasks. Selecting appropriate texts that match learners' interests and proficiency levels ensures accessibility and motivation. Pre-reading activities help activate prior knowledge and prepare students for deeper engagement. Class discussions following the reading encourage oral production, while creative or analytical writing tasks based on the text promote written expression. Collaborative learning, peer feedback, and revision cycles further consolidate learning outcomes. By aligning these activities with language objectives, teachers can transform literature into a dynamic medium for developing expressive, confident, and articulate language users.

Literature holds significant potential as a pedagogical tool to enhance learners' productive skills in speaking and writing. Through offering rich linguistic input, discourse models, prompts for creative and analytic output, and emotional engagement, literary texts can stimulate learners to move from passive reception to active production.

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ISAAK ASIMOVNING “ULAR QANCHALIK ZAVQLANISHGAN EDI” ASARIDA TA'LIMNI O'ZGARTIRUVCHI KUCH IFODASI

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Annotatsiya: Isaak Asimovning “The Fun They Had” (“Ular qanchalik zavqlanishgan edi”, 1951) nomli qisqa hikoyasi ta'lim, texnologiya va insoniy aloqa haqida qisqa, ammo chuqur falsafiy mulohazani o'zida mujassam etadi. Asar taxminiy kelajakda sodir bo'ladi va ikki bola Margi hamda Tommi eski bosma kitobni topib, uning orqali inson o'qituvchilari

bilan birgalikda o'qitilgan o'tmishdagi maktab hayotini kashf etadi. Ushbu maqola hikoyaning tuzilishi, qahramonlari, ramzlari va asosiy g'oyalari yuzasidan badiiy tahlilni o'z ichiga oladi hamda Asimovning yozishdagi maqsadini yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Isaak Asimov, The Fun They Had, ta'lim, texnologiya, insoniy qadriyatlar, badiiy tahlil, ramziylik.

Аннотация: Короткий рассказ Айзека Азимова «The Fun They Had» («Как они веселились», 1951) представляет собой краткое, но глубокое философское размышление о образовании, технологиях и человеческом общении. Действие произведения происходит в предполагаемом будущем, где двое детей -Марги и Томми -находят старую печатную книгу и через неё открывают для себя школьную жизнь прошлого, когда обучение проходило с участием человеческих учителей. В данной статье представлен художественный анализ структуры рассказа, его персонажей, символики и основных идей, а также раскрывается авторский замысел Азимова.

Ключевые слова: Айзек Азимов, The Fun They Had, образование, технологии, человеческие ценности, художественный анализ, символизм.

Annotation: Isaac Asimov's short story "The Fun They Had" (1951) offers a brief yet profound philosophical reflection on education, technology, and human connection. Set in a speculative future, the story follows two children-Margie and Tommy-who discover an old printed book and, through it, learn about the school life of the past, when human teachers guided students. This article provides a literary analysis of the story's structure, characters, symbolism, and main ideas, as well as an exploration of Asimov's purpose in writing it.

Keywords: Isaac Asimov, The Fun They Had, education, technology, human values, literary analysis, symbolism.

Isaak Asimov "The Fun They Had" asarini 1951-yilda yozgan, bu davrda zamonaviy kompyuter texnologiyalari va avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar hali yangi tushuncha edi. Yozuvchi bolalarni uyda mexanik o'qituvchilar ta'lim beradigan kelajakni tasvirlab, texnologik taraqqiyotga nazar tashlagan holda, ta'lim aslida nimani ko'zlashi kerakligi haqida fundamental savollarni qo'yadi. Hikoya juda qisqa ming so'zdan kam bo'lishiga qaramay, uning ma'naviy va intellektual kuchi nihoyatda katta. Margi va Tommi ko'zlari orqali Asimov bizga ikki dunyoni solishtiradi: mexanik ta'limning sovuq, hissiz samaradorligi va inson markazidagi eski maktablarning iliq, jamoaviy hayoti.

Ushbu tadqiqot hikoyani ijtimoiy tanqid va ta'limiy mulohaza sifatida talqin qiladi. Asarda ishlatilgan badiiy vositalar nuqtayi nazar, dialog, ramziylik hamda qahramonlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar (ayniqsa, qiziquvchan Margi va hayotiy tajribaga ega Tommi o'rtasidagi tafovut) tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, hikoya bugungi ta'lim tizimidagi dolzarb holatlar masofaviy ta'lim, shaxsga moslashtirilgan o'qitish dasturlari va texnologiya hech qachon to'liq qondira olmaydigan insoniy ehtiyojlar bilan bog'lanadi.

Tahlilning asosiy maqsadi Asimovning qisqa hikoyasi nafaqat texnologiyalashgan ta'limga tanqid, balki insoniylikka boy, mehr va muloqotga asoslangan maktab hayotining yo'qolishiga bag'ishlangan ogohlantiruvchi asar ekanini ko'rsatishdir.

"The Fun They Had" hikoyasi oddiy, ammo o'yg'a soluvchi voqeadan boshlanadi: 2157-yilda ikki bola Margi va Tommi eski bosma kitobni topishadi. 11 yoshli Margi hikoyaning asosiy nigohidir; Tommi esa undan biroz katta va hayotiyroq fikrlaydigan bola. Ularning jamiyatida "telekitoblar" va "mexanik o'qituvchilar" mavjud har bir bolaga individual dars beruvchi va darhol natija chiqaruvchi mashinalar. Margi o'z o'qituvchisini yoqtirmaydi; u nimanidir yetishmayotganini sezadi, ammo buni aniq so'zlar bilan ifoda eta olmaydi. Tommi esa eski kitobni o'qir ekan, o'tmishdagi umumiy sinflar va tirik o'qituvchilar bilan o'qish g'oyasi unga g'alati tuyuladi.

Hikoya yakunida Margi o'sha eski maktab hayotini tasavvur qiladi va birga o'qish, kulish, o'rganish zavqini his etadi. Shu lahzada hikoya nomi "The Fun They Had" ("Ular qanchalik zavqlanishgan edi") kinoyali, ammo o'ylantiruvchi ma'no kasb etadi: haqiqiy o'rganish quvonchi inson bilan, jamoa bilan birgalikda kechadi.

Hikoya diqqat bilan o'qilganda, Asimovning maqsadi bundan ancha teranroq ekani ayon bo'ladi. U shunchaki o'tgan davrni sog'inmaydi balki "quvonch" va "ta'lim" tushunchalarining chegaralarini sinovdan o'tkazadi, ayniqsa, o'lchovlar va individuallashtirilgan samaradorlik ustuvorlikka aylangan davrda. Hikoyaning ohangi qiziqish va sokin g'amginlik aralash o'quvchini pedagogik jarayonda texnologiyaning o'rnini, uning foyda va zararlarini baholashga undaydi.

Asimovning xarakter yaratish uslubi sodda, biroq samarali. Ikkala bola Margi va Tommi realizmda to'liq ochilgan bosh qahramonlardan ko'ra, muhim g'oyaviy mavzularni yetkazuvchi vositalar sifatida xizmat qiladi. Margi his-tuyg'ularga boy obraz sifatida tasvirlanadi: u mexanik ta'lim tizimi ostida zerikish va yolg'izlikni his qiladi hamda o'qiyotgan eski, jamoaviy maktab g'oyasiga tabiiy tarzda tortiladi. Uning hissiy javobi shunchaki sog'inch emas bu inson tanasiga, ruhiyatiga xos tabiiy pedagogik reaksiya. Margining insoniyligi tasavvur qilish, yo'qotishni his etish va ijtimoiy aloqa uchun sog'inish qobiliyati hikoyaning axloqiy mohiyatini mustahkamlaydi. Tommi esa unga qarama-qarshi, lekin to'ldiruvchi rolni bajaradi. U qiziquvchan, lekin bosiq eski kitobni garajda topadi va uning g'ayritabiiyligini anglay oladi. U Margiga o'sha davrdagi maktab tizimini tushuntirib beradi, shu orqali o'quvchiga eski va yangi ta'lim tizimlari orasidagi kontrastni anglash imkonini yaratadi. Tommining roli izohli va amaliy: u Margi singari hissiy jihatdan murakkab emas, ammo u hikoyaning asosiy ziddiyatini "texnologiya vositasi sifatida" va "ta'lim ijtimoiy jarayon sifatida" ochib beradi.

Mexanik o'qituvchi esa insoniylashtirilmagan, ammo timsol sifatida muhim obraz. U moslashuvchan, samarali, biroq hissiz. Asimov unga texnik mukammallik beradi, lekin insoniy iliqlikni bermaydi. Shu ziddiyat orqali muallif hikoyaning falsafiy muammosini ochadi: texnologik samaradorlik insoniy o'rganishning ijtimoiy mohiyatini almashtirganida, u bo'shliq va ma'naviy sovuqlikni keltirib chiqaradi.

Hikoyadagi ramzlar sodda, ammo kuchli ma'noga ega. Bosma kitob asosiy ramz sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. U moddiy, o'zgarmas va jamoaviy tabiati bilan insoniylikni ifodalaydi bu esa ekranlar va shaxsiy qurilmalar hukmron dunyoda juda qimmatli xususiyatdir. Kitobning jismoniy mavjudligi mashina yashirayotgan haqiqatni ochadi: xotira, umumiy marosimlar (masalan, sahifa aylantirish, sinfda birgalikda o'qish) va insonlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy aloqalar. Yana bir muhim motiv makondir: uy (shaxsiy, yakka, mashina orqali boshqariladigan joy) va maktab (ommaviy, jamoaviy, insoniy muhit) o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshilik. Asimov tasvirlagan kelajakda uylar ta'lim orollari, maktablar esa insoniy uchrashuv nuqtalari sifatida tahlil qilinadi. Bu makoniy ramz hikoyaning axloqiy da'vosini mustahkamlaydi: yakkalanishda o'rganish bilimni ijtimoiy kontekstdan uzib, uni oddiy ma'lumot darajasiga tushirib qo'yadi. Yana bir muhim motiv o'yin va "quvonch". "The Fun They Had" iborasi dastlab arxivdagi so'zdek eshitiladi, ammo hikoya yakunida u axloqiy da'vatga aylanadi. Agar ta'limdagi quvonch kulgi, hayrat, tengdoshlar bilan muloqot, kutilmagan ijtimoiy ilhom inson shakllanishining muhim qismi bo'lsa, unda mashina tomonidan boshqariladigan ta'lim, samaradorligiga qaramay, ta'limning haqiqiy maqsadini yo'qotgan bo'ladi.

Asimovning hikoyasi muayyan ta'lim falsafasini ifodalaydi: bilim insoniy munosabatlardan ajralmasdir. U ta'limni shunchaki ma'lumot uzatish va natija o'lchash jarayoni sifatida emas, balki ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, jamoaviy amaliyot va hissiy ishtirok orqali

o'suvchi jarayon sifatida ko'rsatadi. O'rganish ijtimoiy vositalar orqali shakllanadi, muloqot orqali quriladi va jamoaviylik bilan boyiydi. Agar ta'lim tizimlari Asimovning ogohlantirishlaridan xulosa chiqarmoqchi bo'lsa, bir nechta amaliy jihatlar yuzaga keladi.

Birinchi, o'quv dasturlari avtomatlashtirishga osonlikcha bo'ysunmaydigan hamkorlikka asoslangan topshiriqlarni o'z ichiga olishi kerak bahs-munozaralar, guruh loyihalari, rolli o'yinlar va jamoaviy tadqiqotlar shular jumlasidandir.

Ikkinchi, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash jarayonida ularning munosabat o'rnatish ko'nikmalari tinglash, yo'naltirish, rivojlantiruvchi fikr bildirish va hissiy uyg'unlikni shakllantirish alohida urg'u bilan o'qitilishi lozim.

Uchinchi, ta'limda texnologiya tanlash va joriy etish jarayoni inson markazida bo'lishi kerak. Har bir vosita haqida savol berilishi lozim: "Bu texnologiya insoniy aloqalarni mustahkamlayaptimi yoki ularni yemirmoqdami?"

Isaac Asimovning "The Fun They Had" hikoyasi qisqa bo'lishiga qaramay, chuqur axloqiy va ta'limiy ma'noga ega. Margi va Tommining eski kitob bilan uchrashuvi orqali Asimov shunday fikrni ilgari suradi: ta'limning asl mohiyati insonlararo munosabat va birgalikdagi izlanishda yotadi, texnologik samaradorlik esa bu qadriyatlarining o'rini bosmasligi kerak. Bosma kitob, tasavvurdagi sinf xonasi va bolalarning hissiy reaksiyalari bularning barchasi Asimovning "agar ta'lim to'liq mexanizatsiyalashsa, nimani yo'qotamiz?" degan savoliga adabiy javobidir. Zamonaviy o'qituvchilar va siyosatchilar Asimovning bu oddiy hikoyasini muvozanatga chaqiriq sifatida qabul qilishlari kerak. Texnologiya ta'limga xizmat qilishi mumkin va kerak, biroq u ta'limning ijtimoiy, axloqiy va ijodiy o'lchamlarini soya ostida qoldirmasligi zarur. Asimovning so'nggi, bir oz sog'inch aralash satrlari avvalgi avlodlarning "qanchalik maroqli" o'qigani haqida yuzaki romantizm emas. Bu so'zlar o'rganishdagi quvonch, hamkorlik, qiziqish va jamoaviy kashfiyot insoniyatning o'ziga xos boyligi ekanini eslatadi. Bunday boylikni hech qanday mashina takrorlay olmaydi.

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НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ НОРМ СОВРЕМЕННОГО РУССКОГО ЛИТЕРАТУРНОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация. В данной работе рассматриваются грамматические нормы современного русского языка как система правил, регулирующих функционирование языковых единиц. Особое внимание уделено морфологическим нормам, связанным с употреблением существительных, прилагательных, числительных и глаголов. Приведён анализ трудностей при определении грамматического рода несклоняемых

существительных, образовании падежных форм, выборе кратких и полных форм прилагательных, а также правильном склонении сложных и собирательных числительных. Отмечаются тенденции в развитии современного русского языка, отражающие влияние разговорной речи на литературную норму, например, появление женских форм профессий (редакторка, дизайнерка) и упрощение форм числительных и глаголов в повседневной коммуникации. Подчёркивается значение соблюдения грамматических норм для сохранения культурной и языковой целостности русского литературного языка. [4]

Ключвые слова: грамматическая норма, морфологические нормы, род существительных, формы прилагательных, нормы современного русского языка, синтаксические конструкции, языковая вариативность, литературный стандарт.

Грамматическая норма представляет собой систему правил, регулирующих функционирование языковых единиц на уровне словообразования, словоизменения, а также построения словосочетаний и предложений. В совокупности эти закономерности составляют морфологические и синтаксические нормы. Соблюдение грамматической правильности речи заключается в выборе тех форм и конструкций, которые соответствуют общепринятому литературному стандарту. [4]

Существуют два вида грамматических норм. Это морфологические и синтаксические нормы. Морфологические нормы определяют корректность образования и употребления форм слов. Так, в родительном падеже множественного числа существительных нормативными считаются варианты с нулевым или выраженным окончанием: например, верно *много студентов, учителей*, но неправильно - *кинов, пианинов*. [4]

Морфологические нормы, касающиеся имени существительного, нередко вызывают трудности при выборе правильного варианта в двух случаях: 1) при определении грамматического рода, 2) при образовании падежных форм. [4]

Род представляет собой неизменяемую морфологическую категорию, основанную на противопоставлении трёх классов существительных: мужского (*стол, воин, юноша, ключик*), женского (*книга, ночь*) и среднего рода (*окно, море, время*). Выбор рода существительного проявляется в формах единственного числа и определяет правила согласования с другими членами предложения. [4]

Особое явление русского языка - существительные так называемого общего рода, у которых родовые различия не фиксируются вне контекста. В зависимости от окружения происходит нейтрализация рода: ср. *умница наша* и *умница наш*. [3]

Сложные случаи установления рода существительных:

– к категории мужского рода относятся также несклоняемые существительные.

Их можно разделить на несколько групп:

- а) одушевлённые наименования животных: *малайский тапир, африканский гну*;
- б) одушевлённые существительные со значением лица, при этом родовой признак зависит от реального пола: *опытный референт, талантливый маэстро*;
- в) неодушевлённые существительные, род которых определяется по родовому понятию: *суахили, баскский, панджаби, иврит* (язык); *муссон, ураган* (ветер); *брынза* (сыр); *танго* (танец);
- г) неодушевлённые существительные, род которых устанавливается по аналогии: *байт* (сопоставление со словом «размер»), *шоссе* (по аналогии с «путь» в значении «дорога»), *мате* (влияние мужского рода в языке-источнике), *десерт* (по аналогии с «обед»);
- д) топонимы и имена собственные, род которых определяется по главному слову

или родовому понятию: *современный Карши* (город).

– к категории женского рода относятся также несклоняемые существительные, которые можно подразделить на несколько групп:

а) одушевлённые наименования лиц, при этом родовой признак определяется реальной соотнесённостью с полом: *уважаемая миссис, талантливая мадемуазель*;

б) неодушевлённые существительные, род которых устанавливается по родовому понятию: *манго* (фрукт), *сардины* (рыба), *брокколи* (капуста), *мортаделла* (колбаса), *мошка цеце*;

в) имена собственные, где род определяется по главному слову или родовому понятию: *величественная Фудзияма* (гора), *бурная Волга* (река), *Си-Эн-Эн сообщила* (информационное агентство).

– к категории среднего рода относятся несклоняемые существительные следующих групп:

а) неодушевлённые наименования: *светлое ателье, горячее эспрессо*;

б) субстантивированные слова, то есть слова, перешедшие в разряд существительных из других частей речи: *искреннее «спасибо», радостное «ура», туманное завтра*;

в) имена собственные, род которых определяется по родовому понятию или главному слову: *глубокое Онтарио* (озеро).

– к категории общего рода относятся несклоняемые существительные двух типов:

а) одушевлённые существительные со значением лица, у которых родовая принадлежность выявляется в контексте: *мой коллега оказался требовательным руководителем - моя коллега оказалась требовательной руководительницей; их интервьюер был строг - их интервьюер была строга*; [3]

б) некоторые фамилии, одинаково употребляемые по отношению к лицам разного пола: *Алексей Белых, Марина Белых*.

В современной языковой практике особый интерес представляют варианты рода у наименований профессий и должностей, традиционно относящихся к мужскому роду. Например, такие слова, как профессор, доцент, академик, директор, министр, сохраняют мужской род, даже если речь идёт о женщине: *профессор Иванова прочитала лекцию, новый директор школы приступила к работе*. В данных случаях грамматический род не изменяется, а женская принадлежность выражается через согласование сказуемого или определений. [4]

В то же время в разговорной речи и публицистике всё чаще появляются параллельные женские формы - профессорша, директорша, министерша. Однако в официально-деловом и научном стилях такие варианты признаются разговорными или стилистически сниженными.

Наиболее активно в современном языке закрепляются новообразованные формы на *-ка*: *редакторка, дизайнерка*, которые постепенно входят в употребление, прежде всего в медийной и социалингвистической среде. Тем не менее они ещё не являются строго нормативными и фиксируются словарями преимущественно как вариантные или окказиональные.

Таким образом, при обозначении женщин, занимающих высокие должности, литературная норма пока сохраняет употребление существительных мужского рода с согласованием по смыслу: *наш новый профессор сказала, заместитель директора подписала приказ*.

Падеж представляет собой словоизменительную категорию имени

существительного, выражающуюся в системе противопоставленных рядов форм (именительный, родительный, дательный, винительный, творительный, предложный падежи). Каждая форма отражает синтаксическое отношение имени к другому слову в словосочетании или предложении. Ср.: *тетрадь (чья?) ученицы; иду к (кому?) соседу*.

Единых строгих правил при выборе вариантных окончаний во множественном числе в русском языке не существует. В подобных случаях правильный вариант определяется словарной фиксацией и справочной литературой. Так, нормативными считаются формы: *инженеры - директора, оянт - подосиновиков, носков - чулок*.

Ошибки при употреблении прилагательных чаще всего связаны с «избыточным» образованием степеней сравнения. Так, недопустимы конструкции типа *более лучший* (правильно: *лучший*) или *светлее* вместо *светлей*. Допускаются разные варианты в нейтральном и разговорном стиле: *занят более сложной задачей* (правильное) и *задача потруднее* (разговорное).

Трудности возникают и при выборе между полной и краткой формой прилагательного. Краткая форма в составе сказуемого обозначает временный признак: *дом высок* - характеристика именно в данный момент. Полная форма выражает постоянное свойство: *дом высокий* - общее описание.

В парах кратких форм на *-енен* и *-ен* (*ответственен - ответствен, безнравственен - безнравствен*) в речи все чаще закрепляются более краткие и лаконичные варианты.

Числительные имеют разные способы склонения, и сложные числительные изменяются в обеих частях: например, *триста - трёхсот - трёмстам - тремястами - о трёхстах*; а порядковое числительное *трёхсотый* изменяется так: *трёхсотый - трёхсотого - трёхсотому - трёхсотым - о трёхсотом*. В разговорной речи, особенно в просторечии, склонение сложных числительных часто упрощается или смешиваются разные формы (например, ошибочно *трёхста, о триста, трисотый*). Слово «тысяча» в творительном падеже допустимо употреблять как «тысячью», так и «тысячей». [3]

Частые ошибки при образовании форм глаголов связаны с:

– неправильным формированием форм первого и второго лица, например: *я плещусь, ты распускаешься, я побегу* (ошибочно, поскольку некоторые непереходные глаголы не имеют форм первого и второго лица); [3]

– несоблюдением чередования в корне глагола, особенно у глаголов с двумя вариантами настоящего времени, которые отличаются по стилю или значению: например, *шелестит - шелестает* (разговорное), *капает* (в значении «падает каплями») - *окапывает* (в значении «поливает, смачивает») растения. [3]

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TOHIR MALIK IJODIDA TEOLOGIK TUSHUNCHALAR IFODASI

Rahmatova Sevara Murotovna

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek adabiyotining zabardast vakili Tohir Malik ijodidagi teologik tushunchalarning badiiy va hayot falsafasi sifatida talqini, ularning inson ruhiyati, imon va vijdon bilan bog‘liq mazmuni, ruhiy poklanish va adolat g‘oyalari xalq tiliga yaqinligi tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada adibning asarlaridagi til, uslub va ma’naviy qatlamlarni ochib berishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tohir Malik, teologik tushunchalar, imon, tavba, taqdir, vijdon, badiiy tahlil, ma’naviyat.

Adabiyot har doim inson ruhiyatining oynasi bo‘lib kelgan. Shu bois o‘zbek adabiyotida teologik qarashlar, ya’ni diniy va axloqiy g‘oyalar yozuvchi dunyoqarashining ajralmas qismidir. O‘zbek adabiyotida insonning ma’naviy olamini, e’tiqodini va imon sinovlarini chuqur tasvirlagan ijodkorlardan biri - Tohir Malikdir. Uning asarlari nafaqat adabiy hodisa, balki ma’naviy ogohlik maktabidir. Adib o‘z qahramonlari orqali hayotning murakkab, ba’zan ziddiyatli manzaralarini chizadi. Shu jarayonda u “taqdir”, “tavba”, “gunoh”, “sabr”, “vijdon” kabi teologik tushunchalarni tilning badiiy imkoniyatlari orqali chuqur ifoda etadi. Tohir Malik ijodi orqali o‘quvchi insonning ichki olami, ruhiy iztiroblari, e’tiqodi bilan yuzlashadi. Bu asarlar diniy nasihat emas, balki hayotiy haqiqat va ruhiy o‘zgarishning badiiy ifodasidir. Tohir Malik uchun e’tiqod va vijdon muvozanati – bu insonning ichki tuyg‘usi, ruhiy harakati, o‘zini anglash yo‘lidir. Yozuvchi uchun teologiya - bu insonning ichki dunyosini tahlil etuvchi ruhiy ko‘zgidir. Teologik tushunchalarning badiiy ko‘rinishi Tohir Malik asarlarida badiiy nutqning asosiy qatlamini tashkil etadi. Quyidagi jihatlar bunga yaqqol misol bo‘ladi:

1. “Taqdir” – yozuvchi uchun oldindan belgilangan yo‘l emas, balki insonning o‘zi tanlagan yo‘li.

2. “Tavba” – bu kechirim so‘rash emas, balki o‘z xatosini tan olib, ruhiy o‘zgarish sari tashlangan qadam.

3. “Sabr” – har bir insonning sinovi, taqdir oldidagi bardoshi.

4. “Gunoh” – bu yovuzlik emas, balki insonning zaifligi, uni tuzatish uchun berilgan imkon. Bu tushunchalar yozuvchi asarlarida psixologik holat bilan o‘zaro uyg‘unlashgan. Har bir qahramon o‘z “ichki tavbasi” ni boshidan kechiradi. Yozuvchi diniy so‘zlarni ma’naviy-axloqiy g‘oya bilan birlashtirib, ularni o‘zbek tilining ifoda boyligida yangicha talqin etadi. Til va uslubda teologik qatlam Tohir Malikning tili o‘zbek xalqining tafakkuriga yaqin, ammo unda ilohiy ma’nolar tizimi yashiringan. U ”Qur’on” oyatlaridan bevosita iqtibos bermaydi, biroq ularning mazmunini xalqona so‘z bilan ifodalaydi. O‘quvchi uchun Tohir Malik asarlari ma’naviy saboq, diniy targ‘ibot emas, balki ruhiy tahlil maydonidir. Insonni o‘ylashga, o‘zini ko‘rishga, imon bilan yashashga undaydigan asarlari “Shaytanat” to‘rt qismdan iborat bo‘lgan va keyinchalik filmga moslashtirilgan mashhur roman. “Falak” ilmiy-fantastik janrdagi qissa. “So‘nggi o‘q” qissa va hikoyalardan iborat to‘plam unda gunoh, jazo va kechirim masalalari insoniy dramalar bilan bog‘langan. “Hikmat afandining o‘limi” yozuvchining ilk yirik asari. “Alvido, bolalik” o‘smirlar jinoyat olami hayotini aks ettirgan mashhur asarlaridan biri. “Bir kecha, bir ko‘cha” yana bir taniqli hikoyasi. “Imonlashish umidi” asari bu asar “Mehmon tuyg‘ular” kitobining tuzatilgan ikkinchi nashri hisoblanib, odamzotning oxiratdagi o‘rni niyati va ammallariga bog‘liqligiga qaratilganligi to‘g‘risida yozuvchi til vositasida e’tiqodning badiiy tilini yaratgan. Shu orqali Tohir Malik asarlarida teologik semantika bilan milliy ruh birlashgan. Bu jihat uni nafaqat adabiy, balki ma’naviy hodisaga aylantiradi.

“Shaytanat” asarida yozuvchi insonning gunoh va tavba o‘rtasidagi kurashini nafaqat voqealar orqali, balki til orqali ham ko‘rsatadi. Bunda “shaytanat” dunyosi juda keng bo‘lib, borgan sari bu olamga bilib-bilmay, adashib kirib keluvchilar evaziga kengayaveradi. Maqsad esa bitta – boylik, lekin to‘plangan boylikdan aqalli bir tangani o‘zi bilan u dunyoga olib keta olmasligini anglashmagan. Aynan shu “qo‘lning kiri” uchun vijdonidan kechib shaytonning yo‘rig‘iga kirgan kimsalar o‘zlariga hasad, xiyonat, zulm kabi illatlarni hamroh qilishgan. Roman qahramoni Asadbek obrazida yozuvchi “vijdon azobi” ni teologik jihatdan ochib beradi. Har bir so‘z, ibora - “Alloh saqlasin”, “Taqdirning ishi”, “Tavba qilish kerak” - bu faqat tildagi birlik emas, ruhiy jarayonning ko‘zguvidir. Tohir Malik tili xalqona, ammo ma’naviy jihatdan yuksak. U diniy tushunchalarni o‘quvchining hayotiy tajribasiga yaqinlashtiradi. Shu bois “Shaytanat” faqat jinoyat haqida emas - gunohning ichki og‘rig‘i, insonning iymon sinovi haqidagi asardir.

Yozuvchi asarlarida “shayton” obrazining o‘zi ham ramziy ma’noga ega. Bu – insonning ichidagi nafs, yovuzlik, vasvasa timsoli. Bilamizki nafs insonni yomon ishlarlarga buyuradi. Inson zoti unga quloq soldimi, tamom, nafsining quliga aylanadi. Inson aslida Haqning quli, nafsning quli emas. Asarda “Jalilning “Xudodan qaytibdi” degan gapi ham shunaqa” har qanday ishlarimiz hamda hammamiz uchun Ollohning ajri borligini doimo unutmasligimiz lozim. Zero yozuvchi “Odamiylik mulki ”asarida Kimki o‘zining yaxshi amalidan xursand bo‘lib, yomon amalidan xafa bolsa, u mo‘mindir. Bunday dunyo haqiqatlarini “Imonlashish umidi” asarida ham keng yoritib bergan. “Ozod odam hech bir to‘siqsiz egalik qilishi mumkun bo‘lgan narsaga egadir. Xech bir to‘siqsiz nimaga egalik qilish mumkin? Faqat O‘Z-O‘ZIGA! Agar siz odamning o‘z-o‘ziga egalik qilmay, boshqalarga ham hukm o‘tkazmoqqa jazm etganini ko‘rsangiz, bilingkim, u ozod emasdir. U boshqalarga xokimlik qilishni istadimi, demak, u o‘z istagi - nafs qulidir”¹. Shu orqali adib ma’naviy kurashni badiiy shaklda ifoda etadi. Bugungi adabiyotda bunday tahlil zarur. Chunki, teologik tushunchalar – bu diniy masala emas, balki eng avvalo insoniy ong va axloqning ildizidir.

Tohir Malik teologik tushunchalarni jamiyat axloqining mustahkamlanishiga xizmat qiluvchi vosita sifatida talqin etadi. Uning asarlaridagi ruhiy iztirob, tavba, sabr va e’tiqod kabi g‘oyalar o‘quvchini o‘z vijdoni bilan suhbatga chorlaydi. Yozuvchi nafaqat diniy mavzuni, balki insoniy mas’uliyatni ham markazga qo‘yadi. Yozuvchi diniy tushunchalarni insoniy tajriba, ruhiy iztirob va ma’naviy tozalik bilan bog‘lab, o‘z ijodini falsafiy darajaga ko‘targan. Shu sababli, Tohir Malik asarlari bugungi kunda ham o‘quvchini iymon, sabr, vijdon va adolat kabi abadiy qadriyatlarga chorlaydi.

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, Tohir Malik o‘zbek adabiyotiga teologik tafakkurni badiiy nutqqa singdirgan adib sifatida kirgan bo‘lib, teologik tafakkurning yangi bosqichini boshlab berdi. Uning asarlarida din va hayot, ruhiyat va adolat bir butun holda ko‘riladi. Adib asarlarida teologik motivlar nafaqat diniy ma’rifat, balki milliy o‘zlik va axloqiy ongni shakllantirish vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Shu bois Tohir Malik ijodini o‘rganish adabiy, falsafiy va ma’naviy jihatdan ham muhimdir.

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NARRATIVE PERSPECTIVE AND PSYCHOLOGICAL REALISM IN JAMES JOYCE'S A PORTRAIT OF THE ARTIST AS A YOUNG MAN

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Annotation. This article examines how narrative perspective in James Joyce's *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man* creates a sense of psychological realism. By tracing the gradual shift from external to internal narration, the paper shows how Joyce develops the reader's access to the protagonist's consciousness. The study draws on modernist narrative theory and close reading of the text to illustrate how free indirect discourse, interior monologue, and symbolic imagery form a single artistic system. It argues that Joyce's innovation lies in portraying the growth of self-awareness through language itself, making the novel both a story of artistic formation and an experiment in human perception.

Keywords: narrative perspective, psychological realism, modernism, James Joyce, free indirect discourse, stream of consciousness, interior monologue, consciousness, identity, prose style.

Main text. James Joyce stands among the most influential innovators of twentieth-century fiction. His first novel, *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man* (1916), traces the spiritual and intellectual maturation of Stephen Dedalus from early childhood to the threshold of adulthood. The power of this work lies not in external events but in its method: Joyce gradually replaces an omniscient narrator with the shifting perspective of Stephen's inner life. Although James Joyce's novel belongs to early twentieth-century modernism, its narrative techniques continue to shape the methods and theoretical focus of modern literary studies. Understanding how narrative form itself conveys psychological truth is essential to grasping the novel's modernist vision.

Theoretical Background. Traditional realism in nineteenth-century prose relied on an objective narrator who described the world from a single, external viewpoint. Modernist writers such as Henry James, Virginia Woolf, and Joyce rejected this stability, turning instead to the fluidity of perception [3, p. 25].

According to Genette's narratology, *A Portrait* demonstrates a progressive movement from an external to an internal mode of narration [2, p. 71]. Dorrit Cohn defines this blend of narrator and character voice as "transparent minds," where the reader enters a consciousness rather than merely observing it [1, p. 22]. Joyce achieves precisely this effect: the narrator's language echoes the rhythms of Stephen's thought, letting us experience the world through a mind in formation [4, p. 103].

Development of Perspective in the Novel. Joyce's art lies in letting the style grow with the boy.

Childhood. The novel opens in the voice of infancy: "Once upon a time and a very good time it was there was a moocow coming down along the road..." [5, p. 3]. The sentence is simple, musical, and repetitive. It belongs to the world of sound rather than logic, so the reader perceives reality as a child might - directly and without commentary.

Adolescence. When Stephen is unjustly punished at Clongowes, the language already blends narration and thought: "It was cruel and unfair, and he had told himself that he would tell the rector on Father Dolan" [5, p. 47]. This is free indirect discourse in practice: a third-

person voice carrying first-person emotion. We sense Stephen's indignation without quotation marks or explanation - a hallmark of psychological realism.

Adulthood. By the final chapter, narration becomes pure interior monologue: "Welcome, O life! I go to encounter for the millionth time the reality of experience..." [5, p. 252]. Now the boundary between narrator and character has disappeared. The novel ends inside Stephen's consciousness, and language itself becomes the medium of self-creation.

Techniques of Psychological Realism. Joyce achieves depth of inner life through several interrelated techniques.

1. Free indirect discourse. In the Christmas dinner scene, emotion is transmitted through detail rather than commentary: "They were shouting across the table and Uncle Charles was trying to make peace between them. Dante's white face quivered with passion" [5, p. 36]. The reader hears the family's tension through Stephen's frightened perception - realism of feeling, not of fact [3, p. 90].

2. Stream of consciousness. Joyce often records thought as it occurs: "The faint smell of the grease still clung to his fingers... Why did he always feel this strange ache of pity?" [5, p. 119]. The syntax follows association, not grammar, capturing the irregular pulse of emotion [3, p. 132].

3. Symbolic imagery. Symbols of water, light, and flight accompany each turning point. When Stephen sees the bird-girl on the beach, sensory beauty fuses with revelation: "A girl stood before him in midstream, alone and still, gazing out to sea. Her long slender bare legs were delicate as a crane's..." [5, p. 185]. The vision becomes both erotic and spiritual - the language of awakening rather than description [4, p. 157].

Through these devices Joyce constructs a living psychology on the page, giving form to consciousness itself.

Joyce's Modernist Innovation. In *A Portrait*, perspective is not only a stylistic choice but a statement about freedom. As Stephen declares, "I will not serve that in which I no longer believe" [5, p. 240].

The disappearance of the authorial voice parallels this rebellion: both artist and character seek autonomy. Joyce's narrative experiments paved the way for later modernists - Woolf, Faulkner, and others - who continued exploring the limits of representing thought [2, p. 88]. His psychological realism replaced external observation with the drama of inner life.

Conclusion. Joyce's manipulation of narrative perspective transforms the traditional novel into a study of consciousness. From the innocent rhythm of childhood to the complex introspection of adulthood, *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man* reveals how language can chart the formation of mind. Through free indirect discourse, stream of consciousness, and symbolic structure, Joyce discovers a new kind of realism - one that sees truth not in events but in perception itself [4, p. 184].

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O'ZBEK TILINING IJTIMOIIY HAYOTDAGI O'RNI VA YOSH AVLOD ONGIDAGI TA'SIRI

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Xorijiy til va adabiyoti yo'nalishi talabasi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilining tarixiy rivojlanishi, uning ijtimoiy hayotdagi rolini tahlil qilish orqali, tilning davlat boshqaruvi, ta'lim, ommaviy axborot vositalari va yoshlar ongidagi ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Metod sifatida kuzatuv, tahlil va taqqoslash usullari qo'llanildi. Natijalardan ma'lum bo'lishicha, til faqat muloqot vositasi emas, balki millatning madaniy va ma'naviy yuzidir. Maqolada yoshlar orasida til madaniyatini shakllantirishga doir taklif va mulohazalar ham bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbek tili, davlat tili, til madaniyati, ta'lim, yoshlar, ijtimoiy hayot, milliy o'zlik, til bayrami.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается историческое развитие узбекского языка и его роль в общественной жизни. Через анализ влияния языка на государственное управление, образование, средства массовой информации и сознание молодёжи показано, что язык является не только средством общения, но и культурным и духовным лицом нации. В статье также приведены предложения и соображения по формированию культуры речи среди молодёжи.

Ключевые слова: узбекский язык, государственный язык, культура речи, образование, молодёжь, общественная жизнь, национальная идентичность, праздник языка.

Abstract: This article analyzes the historical development of the Uzbek language and its role in social life. By examining the language's influence on state administration, education, mass media, and youth consciousness, it is shown that language is not only a means of communication but also the cultural and spiritual identity of the nation. The article also presents proposals and reflections on developing speech culture among young people.

Key words: Uzbek language, state language, speech culture, education, youth, social life, national identity, language day.

Har bir millatning milliy o'zligini belgilab beruvchi eng muhim omillardan biri - bu uning ona tilidir. Til nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki xalqning tarixiy xotirasi, madaniyati, an'anasi va hayotiy qarashlarini o'z ichiga olgan boy ma'naviy meros hisoblanadi.

O'zbek tili - buyuk o'tmishga ega, ildizlari chuqur tarixga borib taqaladigan tillardan biri bo'lib, 1989 yil 21 oktyabrda "O'zbek tilining davlat tili sifatida" e'tirof etilishi orqali uning maqomi yanada yuksak pog'onaga ko'tarildi.

Ushbu maqolada tilning ijtimoiy hayotdagi roli, yoshlar ongidagi o'rni, ta'lim va axborot makonidagi mavqei, shuningdek, uni rivojlantirishga oid amaliy choralar tahlil qilinadi.

Til har qanday jamiyatning madaniy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy hayotida muhim o'rin tutadi. Ayniqsa, davlat tili maqomiga ega bo'lgan til - xalqning boshqaruv, ta'lim, fan va ommaviy axborot tizimlaridagi birdamligini ta'minlovchi asosiy vositadir. Mustaqillik yillarida O'zbekistonda davlat tilini rivojlantirish, uning nufuzi va qo'llanish doirasini kengaytirish bo'yicha tizimli chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirildi.

Bugungi globallashuv va axborot texnologiyalari asrida o'z ona tilini asrash va uni yanada rivojlantirish dolzarb masalaga aylanmoqda. Tillararo raqobat kuchaygan bir

sharoitda o‘zbek tili o‘z mavqeini saqlab qolish, yosh avlod ongi va ijtimoiy ongda barqaror o‘rin egallashi uchun yangicha yondashuvlarni, ilmiy asoslangan til siyosatini talab qiladi.

Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek tilining bugungi kundagi holati, uni o‘rganish va qo‘llashdagi muammolar va imkoniyatlar, shuningdek, yoshlarda ona tiliga nisbatan mas‘uliyatni shakllantirish yo‘llari ilmiy tahlil etiladi.

Ushbu tadqiqotda o‘zbek tilining ijtimoiy hayotdagi o‘rni, ta‘lim tizimidagi mavqei va yoshlar ongidagi ta‘sirini o‘rganish maqsadida quyidagi ilmiy-amaliy metodlardan foydalanildi:

1. Kuzatuv usuli: O‘zbek tilining jamiyatdagi qo‘llanilish holatlarini tahlil qilishda birinchi navbatda tabiiy va maqsadli kuzatuv olib borildi. Davlat idoralari, ta‘lim muassasalari va ommaviy axborot vositalarida tildan foydalanish ko‘lami kuzatildi. Maktablarda o‘tkazilgan til bayrami tadbirlari, kitobxonlik kechalari va tanlovlar orqali yoshlar ongida tilga bo‘lgan munosabatni kuzatish imkoni paydo bo‘ldi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda (Telegram, Instagram, YouTube) o‘zbek tilidagi kontentlarning tarqalishi va foydalanuvchilar munosabati kuzatildi.

2. Tahlil va kontent tahlili: O‘rganilayotgan mavzu doirasidagi turli materiallar, qonun hujjatlari, dunyoqarashni shakllantiruvchi ommaviy nutqlar, ta‘lim dasturlari va mediamatnlar tahlil qilindi: “Davlat tili haqida”gi qonun, Prezident farmonlari va konsepsiya hujjatlari o‘rganildi. Ta‘lim muassasalaridagi “O‘zbek tili” fanidan darsliklar va o‘quv qo‘llanmalar kontent tahliliga tortilib, ulardagi lingvistik yundalishlar, tarbiyaviy jihatlar va til madaniyati elementlari o‘rganildi. Blogerlar va ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali tarqalgan tildagi nutq (mulohazalar, videolar) mazmun va uslub jihatidan tahlil qilindi.

3. So‘rovnoma va intervyular (fokus guruh shaklida): Tadqiqotning amaliy qismida o‘quvchi va talabalar o‘rtasida so‘rovnoma o‘tkazildi. Savollar asosan tilga munosabat, uning foydalanish doirasi va kelajagi haqidagi fikrlarga qaratildi.

50 nafar 10–11-sinf o‘quvchilari va 30 nafar talabalar ishtirokida so‘rovnoma o‘tkazildi. Quyidagi savollarga javob olindi:

O‘zbek tilida fikr yuritish darajasi qanday?

Sizningcha, til qanday sohalarda keng qo‘llanilmoqda?

Televideniye va internetda o‘zbek tili kontentiga bo‘lgan munosabatingiz?

O‘zbek tili kelajagi haqida fikringiz?

Shuningdek, ikki nafar ona tili o‘qituvchisi va bir tilshunos olim bilan qo‘shimcha intervyular tashkil etildi.

4. Qiyosiy tahlil usuli: O‘zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi qo‘llanilish darajasi boshqa davlatlar - xususan, Qozog‘iston, Qirg‘iziston, Turkiya kabi mamlakatlarda davlat tilining rivojlanishi bilan taqqoslandi. Bu qiyosiy yondashuv o‘zbek tilining istiqbolini baholashga yordam berdi.

5. Ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish: Mavzuga oid ilmiy va metodik adabiyotlar - tilshunoslik, ijtimoiy lingvistika, sosiologiya, ta‘lim metodikasiga oid risolalar o‘rganildi. Xususan, tilning ijtimoiy funksiyalari, yoshlarda milliy o‘zlikni shakllantirishdagi roli bo‘yicha ilmiy qarashlar tahlil etildi.

Qo‘llanilgan metodlar ushbu maqolada nazariy va amaliy tahlillarni sifatli olib borish, xulosalarni asosli va dolzarb qilib shakllantirish imkonini berdi. Xususan, yoshlar ongida tilga bo‘lgan munosabat, ta‘limda undan foydalanish darajasi va ommaviy axborot vositalaridagi namoyon bo‘lishi haqida aniq tasavvur hosil qilindi.

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O.GENRINING "SEHRGARLARNING SOVG‘ASI" HIKOYASIDA SEVGI VA FIDOYILIK G‘OYASI

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Annotatsiya: Amerika adabiyoti tarixida qisqa hikoya janri alohida o‘rin egallaydi. Ushbu janrning eng yorqin namoyandalaridan biri O. Genri (1862-1910) bo‘lib, uning ijodida insoniylik, muhabbat va fidoyilik g‘oyalari markaziy o‘rinda turadi. Adibning “Sehrgarlarning sovg‘asi” (1905) hikoyasi sevgi va sadoqatning ramziy ifodasiga aylangan. Ushbu maqolada hikoyaning badiiy xususiyatlari, ramziy ma‘nolari hamda unda ilgari surilgan insoniy qadriyatlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: O. Genri, qisqa hikoya, sevgi, fidoyilik, ramz, kinoya, insoniylik, go‘zallik, sadoqat.

Abstract: The short story genre holds a special place in the history of American literature. One of its most prominent representatives is O. Henry (1862–1910), whose works center around themes of humanity, love, and devotion. His story “*The Gift of the Magi*” (1905) has become a symbolic expression of love and loyalty. This article analyzes the artistic features, symbolic meanings, and humanistic values presented in the story.

Keywords: O. Henry, short story, love, devotion, symbol, irony, humanity, beauty, loyalty.

Аннотация: Жанр короткого рассказа занимает особое место в истории американской литературы. Одним из самых ярких его представителей является О. Генри (1862–1910), в чьем творчестве центральное место занимают идеи человечности, любви и самоотверженности. Его рассказ «*Дары волхвов*» (1905) стал символическим выражением любви и преданности. В статье анализируются художественные особенности произведения, его символическое значение и отраженные в нем гуманистические ценности.

Ключевые слова: О. Генри, короткий рассказ, любовь, самоотверженность, символ, ирония, человечность, красота, преданность.

Amerika adabiyoti tarixida hikoya janri, ayniqsa XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlarida, o‘zining eng yuksak cho‘qqisiga chiqdi. Shu davrda O. Genri nomi alohida porlab turadi. Uning hikoyalari oddiy odamlarning hayoti, orzulari, quvonchlari va dardlarini jonli va samimiy tarzda tasvirlaydi. O. Genrining yozish uslubi hayotiy realizm, yumor va kutilmagan yakunlari bilan ajralib turadi.

Adib ijodining eng mashhur namunalaridan biri “Sehrgarlarning sovg‘asi” hikoyasi. Bu asarda insoniy tuyg‘ularning eng sof, eng samimiy ko‘rinishi gavdalanadi. Hikoya kambag‘al, ammo bir-birini chin dildan sevuvchi er-xotin Jim va Della hayoti haqida. Yangi yil arafasida ular bir-biriga sovg‘a qilish uchun o‘zlaridagi eng qimmat narsadan voz kechadilar. Della o‘zining uzun, chiroyli sochini sotib, eriga soati uchun zanjir oladi. Jim esa bobosidan qolgan eng qimmat merosi - soatini sotib, Dellaga soch taroqlarini sovg‘a qiladi.

Mazkur vaziyat o‘zida sevgi va fidoyilikning eng oliy darajasini mujassam etadi. Sovg‘alarning o‘z amaliy ahamiyatini yo‘qotganligi kinoya vositasida tasvirlanadi, ammo bu holat asarning mazmuniy qiymatini yanada chuqurlashtiradi. Yozuvchi moddiy narsalar emas, balki ma‘naviy boylik - sadoqat va muhabbat inson hayotining haqiqiy qadriyatlari ekanini ta‘kidlaydi.

O. Genri hikoyalarida ramz va kinoya muhim badiiy vosita sifatida qo‘llanadi.

Asarda:

Soch - ayollik, go‘zallik va sadoqat timsoli;

Soat - vaqt va hayotning o'tkinchiligini bildiruvchi ramz;

Sovg'alar - chin sevgi va fidoyilik ifodasi;

Sehrgarlar - qadimiy donishmandlar timsoli bo'lib, ular orqali Jim va Della zamonaviy fidoyilar sifatida talqin etiladi.

Bu ramzlar bir butun holda insoniy fazilatlarning abadiyligini va sevgi qadriyatlarining o'tmasligini ifodalaydi. Hikoyaning kutilmagan yakuni esa kinoyaviy ohangda, hayotning paradoksal mohiyatini ko'rsatadi.

O. Genrining "Sehrgarlarning sovg'asi" hikoyasi ijtimoiy jihatdan ham dolzarbdir. U jamiyatda moddiy boylikka haddan ortiq e'tibor berishning ma'nosizligini fosh etadi. Adib fikricha, insonning haqiqiy boyligi - bu sevgi, sadoqat, insoniylik va o'zgalarga mehr bilan munosabatda bo'lishdir. Shuning uchun ham hikoya o'quvchini axloqiy jihatdan poklanishga, insoniy fazilatlarni qadrlashga undaydi.

"Sehrgarlarning sovg'asi" qisqa hajmiga qaramay, mazmunan chuqur, g'oyaviy jihatdan universal asardir. Unda insoniy tuyg'ular, fidoyilik, muhabbat va ma'naviyatning ustuvorligi yuksak badiiy ifodasini topgan. Hikoya nafaqat O. Genrining ijodida, balki jahon adabiyotida ham qisqa hikoya janrining eng mukammal namunalaridan biri sifatida tan olingan. Bugungi kunda ham u o'quvchilar qalbiga chuqur ta'sir etadi va abadiy insoniy qadriyatlarni ulug'lashda davom etmoqda.

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JAHON ADABIYOTIDA "FANTASTIKA" BADIY KATEGORIYASIGA OID NAZARIY QARASHLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada "fantastika" tushunchasining jahon adabiy jarayonidagi nazariy talqinlari tahlil qilinadi. Unda fantastik elementlarning estetik va gnoseologik mohiyati, ularning adabiy asarlarda badiiy haqiqatni ifodalashdagi o'rni hamda davr tafakkuriga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Maqolada G'arb va Sharq adabiyoti namunalari, xususan, Gomer, Dante, Servantes, Gyugo, Shekspir, Tolstoy, Kafka, Jorj Oruell, J.R.R. Tolkien kabi yozuvchilarning asarlarida fantastikaning shakllanishi va evolyutsiyasi nazariy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, fantastikaning romantizm, modernizm va postmodernizm davrlaridagi poetik transformatsiyasi, uning falsafiy hamda ijtimoiy mazmun bilan uyg'unlashuvi yoritiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari adabiy tahlil uchun "fantastika" kategoriyasining universal estetik va madaniy funksiyasini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: fantastika, badiiy kategoriya, jahon adabiyoti, estetik tafakkur, modernizm, postmodernizm, badiiy haqiqat, mifopoetika, adabiy evolyutsiya, poetik transformatsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются теоретические взгляды на понятие «фантастика» в мировой литературе. Рассматриваются эстетическая и гносеологическая сущность фантастических элементов, их роль в отражении

художественной реальности и влияние на мировоззрение эпохи. На основе произведений западной и восточной литературы - Гомера, Данте, Сервантеса, Гюго, Шекспира, Толстого, Кафки, Джорджа Оруэлла, Дж. Р. Р. Толкина - исследуется формирование и эволюция фантастики с теоретической точки зрения. Особое внимание уделяется поэтическим трансформациям фантастики в эпохи романтизма, модернизма и постмодернизма, а также её философскому и социальному содержанию. Результаты исследования способствуют выявлению универсальных эстетических и культурных функций категории «фантастика» в литературном анализе.

Ключевые слова: фантастика, художественная категория, мировая литература, эстетическое мышление, модернизм, постмодернизм, художественная реальность, мифопоэтика, литературная эволюция, поэтическая трансформация.

Abstract: This article analyzes theoretical perspectives on the concept of “fantasy” as a literary category in world literature. It explores the aesthetic and epistemological nature of fantastic elements, their role in expressing artistic reality, and their influence on the worldview of the era. Drawing upon examples from both Western and Eastern literary traditions - including the works of Homer, Dante, Cervantes, Hugo, Shakespeare, Tolstoy, Kafka, George Orwell, and J. R. R. Tolkien - the paper examines the formation and evolution of the fantastic from a theoretical standpoint. Special attention is given to the poetic transformations of fantasy during the periods of Romanticism, Modernism, and Postmodernism, as well as its philosophical and social dimensions. The findings contribute to understanding the universal aesthetic and cultural functions of the “fantasy” category in literary analysis.

Key words: fantasy, literary category, world literature, aesthetic thought, modernism, postmodernism, artistic reality, mythopoetics, literary evolution, poetic transformation

Dunyo adabiy jarayonida yangi yo‘nalishlar yoki uslublarning shakllanishi va taraqqiyoti nafaqat adabiy hamda umumiy madaniy makonda sodir bo‘layotgan o‘zgarishlar, balki jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy vosealar bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir. Turli xalqlar jamiyatchiligida sodir bo‘layotgan ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik va madaniy jarayonlarni tasvirlash uchun adiblar yangi va yangi usullarga murojaat qilishadiki, natijada adabiyotda oldingilaridan farq qiluvchi o‘zgacha yo‘nalishlar paydo bo‘lishiga sababchi bo‘ladilar. Adabiy jarayondagi ana shunday hodisalardan biri bu fantastik adabiyotning paydo bo‘lishidir.

Fantastika atamasi grekcha phantastikē - tasavvur qila olish mahorati so‘zidan kelib chiqqan bo‘lib, xayolan tasvirlash san‘atini anglatadi. Fantastikaning tasvir sohasi real hayot emas, balki turmush haqidagi umumiy tasavvurdan kelib chiqadigan hayotdir.

Ma‘lumki, yozma adabiyotning ilk ko‘rinishi xalq og‘zaki ijodi bo‘lib, folklor doim fantastika bilan bevosita bog‘liq ravishda rivojlangan. Fantastika aslida poetik ijod rivojlanishining ilk bosqichlaridayoq, yani folklor namunalari paydo bo‘lgan davrdan boshlab turli afsona va ertaklarning badiiy mazmuni bilan uzviy bog‘langan shaklda mavjud bo‘lgan. Keyinchalik, yozma adabiyot paydo bo‘lganidan keyin, fantastika adiblarning tasavvur qila olish mahoratlariga bevosita bog‘liq shakllana boshladi. Bu jarayonda endi afsona va ertaklarning badiiy mazmuni mualliflar tomonidan qayta ishlanishi fenomeni kuzatila boshlandi.

XX asrga kelib dunyo adabiyotshunoslik ilmida fantastika, ilmiy fantastika, fentezi, fantastik realizm, sehrli realizm kabi tushunchalar paydo bo‘ldiki, bu mazkur atamalarning mazmun-mohiyat va mantiqiy chegarasini, badiiy kategoriya sifatidagi aniq hamda uzil-kesil ta‘rif va tavsifini belgilab olish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqardi. Zero ularning hammasida folklor arxetiplarga murojaat qilish hodisasi kuzatiladi. Qolaversa, ko‘plab tadqiqotchilar va kitobxonlar mazkur yo‘nalishlarda yozilgan badiiy asarlar haqida ilmiy munozaralar

jarayonida ularning qaysi uslubda yozilgani, yozuvchilar oldiga qo‘ygan badiiy vazifalarda bu uslublarning qanday ahamiyati borligi masalasida ayrim xatolarga yo‘l qo‘yishmoqdaki, bu masalaning faktik yechimini topish, ko‘ndalang turgan muammoli savollarga javob topish zaruriyatini tug‘diradi.

Badiiy adabiyotdagi fantastika kategoriyasi haqida ko‘plab adabiyotshunoslar izlanishlar olib bordilarki, ularning nazariy qarashlari bizga fantastikaning asl mohiyatini anglab olishga imkon beradi. S.Todorov turli tizim, tartib-qoida va tamoyil va rivojlanish darajasiga ega ikki olamning o‘zaro to‘qnashuvini fantastika janrining farqlantiruvchi bir belgisi sifatida ko‘radi. Uning fikricha, fantastika o‘quvchining oddiy olam va g‘ayrioddiy mo‘jizalar olamini o‘zaro taqqoslashi jarayonidagi ikkilanishlar paytida yuzaga keladi [1].

B.Mixaylovskiyning ta‘rificha: “Badiiy adabiyotda fantastika real voqelikka mos kelmaydigan ishonib bo‘lmas hodisalarning tasviri, to‘qima obrazlarning kiritilishi bo‘lib, bunda san‘atkor tomonidan tabiiy shakllar va tabiat qonunlarining buzilishi yaqqol kuzatiladi” [2].

XX asr ikkinchi yarmiga kelib fantastik adabiyotga mustaqil adabiy hodisa sifatida tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslikning tadqiqot ob‘ekti sifatida yondosha boshlandi. Bu borada rus adabiyotshunoslari olib borgan ishlar alohida ahamiyatga ega. Xususan, G.I. Gurevichning 2 ta kitobi ilmiy fantastika tadqiqotiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lsa [1], E.P. Brandis o‘zining qator ilmiy ishlarini fransuz fantast-yozuvchisi Jyul Vern ijodiga va ilmiy fantastik romanchilikning rivojlanish masalalariga bag‘ishlagan. Shuningdek, A.F. Britikov sobiq sovet ittifoqi rus adiblari qalamiga mansub romanlar tadqiqi bilan shug‘ullangan va birinchi bo‘lib mamlakatdagi ilmiy-fantastik adabiyotni tarixiy-adabiy jihatdan tadqiq etgan. Uning mazkur tadqiqoti 1917-1967-yillarda yozilgan fantastik adabiy asarlarga bag‘ishlangan. S.L. Koshelev esa 20-asrning 50-60-yillari ingliz adabiyotidagi ayrim yozuvchilarning fantastik asarlaridagi falsafiy qarashlarni o‘rgandi. Shuni alohida ta‘kidlash lozimki, mazkur adabiyotshunos olimlar o‘z tadqiqotlarida birinchilardan bo‘lib ushbu yo‘nalishning badiiy usullari va janr xususiyatlarini tizimlashtirishga uringanlar. Biroq, hozir ham fantastik adabiyotning lingvistik, kompozitsion, syujet xususiyatlari ko‘plab tadqiqotchilarning ilmiy qiziqishlari markazida bo‘lib qolmoqda.

I.V. Golovacheva [5]. esa o‘z monografiyasida fantastikaga adabiyotning maxsus ko‘rinishi sifatida qarashni taklif etadi.

Mahalliy va xorijiy adabiyotshunoslikda umuman fantastik adabiyotning, xususan, uning janr turlarining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi bilan bog‘liq masalalarni ko‘rib chiqadigan bir qator tadqiqotlar mavjud. Bunda ilmiy fantastika va fantaziya yo‘nalishlariga alohida e‘tibor beriladi. Ta‘kidlash joizki, fantastika zamonaviy adabiy tanqidda keng talqin qilinadigan atamalardan biridir. Bu atama tasvirni yaratishda obrazli ifoda vositalari tizimini va fantaziya etakchi mavzu bo‘lib xizmat qiladigan adabiyot turini hamda adabiyotning katta bir yo‘nalishini o‘z ichiga oladi. L.I.Timofeev ta‘kidlaganidek, “fantastika bu ilgari o‘rganilgan real hayot faktlari asosida xayolotda tug‘ilgan hayoliy g‘oyalar va tasvirlar dunyosi”dir.

S.P. Belokurovaning ta‘kidlashicha, “fantastika - bu o‘ziga xos badiiy tasvir turiga asoslangan fantastika turi bo‘lib, u quyidagilar bilan tavsiflanadi: yuqori darajadagi odatiylik; voqelikning meyorlari, mantiqiy aloqalari va qonunlarini buzish, fantastika o‘rnatish, badiiy adabiyotga yo‘naltirilganlik, o‘ylab topilgan “ajoyib” olamlarni yaratish” [4]. Xuddi shu nuqtayi nazarni I.V. Golovacheva quvvatlagan holda, fantastikaning o‘ziga xosligini ta‘kidlaydi [5]. Olimlar fantastika haqidagi tushunchaga asoslanib, an‘anaviy va sintetik janrlarni (masalan, gotika qo‘rquvi, fantastika, ilmiy fantastika, utopiya) g‘ayrioddiy, begona, deviant, ekstremalni ifodalashning maxsus usuli sifatida - haddan tashqari yoki aksincha, kam

deb hisoblaydilar. Yozuvchidan yozuvchiga meros bo'lib qolgan ma'no hosil qiluvchi "genetik xususiyatlar", uning fikricha, klassik fantastik obrazlarning (arvoh, nusxa, yirtqich hayvon) vizual imkoniyatlaridir[8].

T.A. Balashova quyidagi ta'rifni taklif qiladi: "badiiy adabiyot - bu badiiy tafakkurning maxsus turi tomonidan yaratilgan va empirik dunyoni o'zgartirishga asoslangan voqelikni badiiy ochish funksiyasini bajaradigan adabiyot turi", ya'ni fantastika (jumladan, ilmiy fantastika) – "turli janrdagi bir qator og'zaki badiiy matnlarning ma'lum bir tematik umumiyligi", shuningdek, "ilmiy, falsafiy va haqiqatni tushunish o'yinini o'z ichiga olgan intellektual va badiiy eksperiment" [7]. E.M.Neyolov fantaziyaning adabiy janr deb hisoblab, undagi inson va olam obrazi "sehrli ertak tamoyillariga" bo'ysunadi, deb ta'kidlaydi. Olimning fikricha, "haqiqatning sehrli ertak modeli... hayratlanarli darajada yaqin bo'lib chiqadi, bu eng avvalo, ertakdagi kabi (agar uning natural-falsafiy tomoni haqida gapiradigan bo'lsak) ilmiy fantastikada "odam (qabila) – tabiat" qarama-qarshiligi markaziy o'rinni egallashi bilan bog'liq" [9]. L.G. Fishman o'zining "badiiy adabiyot va fuqarolik jamiyati" monografiyasida ilmiy fantastikani siyosiy va sotsiologik tushunchalarni aks ettiruvchi janr sifatida izohlaydi. Olimning fikricha, fantastika (ilmiy fantastika va fentezi), XX asrning eng "tanilgan" yo'nalishi, "bunda [asr] o'zini adekvat ifodalash uchun eng yaxshi vositalarni topdi", Yevropa jamiyatlarida "fantastika ilgari mafkura va utopiya o'ynagan rolni o'ynay boshladi". Boshqa tadqiqotchilar ham badiiy adabiyotning ijtimoiy mohiyatiga e'tibor berishadi. Shunday qilib, T.V. Timoshenko: "fantastika o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra ijtimoiy-madaniy dinamikani aks ettiradi", deb ta'kidlaydi [6].

Xorijiy adabiyotshunoslikda fantastika ta'rifiga yondashuvlarda ham xilma-xillik mavjud. Masalan, S.Todorovning fikricha, quyidagi uchta shart bajarilsa, adabiy asarni fantastik janrga kiritish mumkin:

adabiy matn o'quvchini fantastik dunyosini tirik odamlar olami deb bilishga majbur qilishi va tasvirlangan voqealarning tabiiy va o'quvchi g'ayritabiiy tasvirlari o'rtasida tanlov qilishda ikkilanishni boshdan kechirishi kerak;

shu kabi ikkinishlarni qahramonlar ham boshdan kechirishlari kerak, buning natijasida ikkilanishlar tasvirning mavzusiga, asar mavzularidan biriga aylanadi;

o'quvchi matnga nisbatan ma'lum bir pozitsiyani egallashi kerak: ham allegorik, ham "poetik" talqindan voz kechishi kerak [10].

Shunday qilib, S.Todorovning fikricha, hodisaning tabiiy yoki g'ayritabiiy xarakterga ega ekanligi haqidagi qahramon va o'quvchining ikkilanishlari orqali fantastika yaratiladi.

S.Todorov "fantastika avtonom janr emas, balki ikki janr: ajoyib va g'ayrioddiy" o'rtasidagi chegara ekanligini ta'kidlab, "fantastik-g'ayrioddiy" kabi janrlarni bo'linishini belgilab beradi ("haqiqat qonunlari buzilmaydi va tasvirlangan hodisalarni tushuntirish mumkin bo'lgan o'ziga xoslikni yaratadi); fantastik-ajoyib (tabiatning boshqa qonunlari mavjudligini taxmin qilish kerak, ularning yordami bilan tushuntirish mumkin bo'lgan hodisa)»; sof shaklda mo'jizaviy [11].

R.Lachmann o'zining "fantastika nutqlari" asarida S.Todorovning g'oyalarini rivojlantiradi. Tadqiqotchi badiiy adabiyotning quyidagi xususiyatlarini aniqlaydi: 1) "mavjud tartib asoslarini aniqlash", "inson tabiati haqidagi hozirgi bilimlarni inversiya qilish"; 2) "insonning o'lchovsizligi"; 3) "o'ziniki - boshqasini" qarama-qarshiligi; 4) "real - noreal" qarama-qarshilik, paradokslilik [12].

Biz L.A.Chexlovaning dissertatsiya tadqiqotida qilingan xulosaga qo'shilamiz: "...g'aroyib asarni biron bir o'ziga xos xususiyatning mavjudligi bilan aniqlab bo'lmaydi, chunki fantaziya bir qator mezonlar (tuzilish, mavzu, asardagi fantastik obrazning roli va boshqalar) bilan tavsiflanadi. Fantastikani tushunish zamonaviy davr va madaniyatga mos

kelishi va obyektiv voqelikni idrok etishga asoslanishi kerak. Fantaziyani aniqlash uchun uning paydo bo'lgan vaqtini, asardagi fantastikaning roli va funksiyasini, o'quvchining "ishtirokini" hisobga olish kerak. Shunday qilib, fantastika tushunchasining o'zi nisbiylik bilan tavsiflanadi» [13].

Shunday qilib, fantastika - bu voqelikni qayta ishlash usuli bo'lib, unda hayotiy haqiqat yozuvchi tomonidan shu darajada qayta ishlanadiki, muallif mavjudlik voqelikning bir qator elementlarini buzishdan tortib, to voqelikni keng ko'lamli qayta qurish darajasigacha boradi. Albatta, har qanday adabiy asarda ham badiiy to'qima mavjud bo'ladiku, degan o'rinli savol tug'ilishi mumkin. gap shundaki, badiiy to'qimada hayotiy voqelikka zid keluvchi unsurlarga yo'l qo'yilmaydi, ya'ni to'qib chiqarilgan voqea-hodisalar ham hayotiy voqealarga zid emas. Fantastikada esa real hayotda sodir bo'lishi mumkin bo'lmagan hodisalar tasviriga ham yo'l qo'yiladi.

Zamonaviy adabiy tanqidda fantastik adabiyotning ikki yo'nalishga bo'linishi yo'lga qo'yilgan: fantastika (ilmiy fantastika) va fentezi. Biroq bizning fikrimizcha, bu bo'linish yetarlicha emas. Zero, fantastikaning boshqa yo'nalishdagi asarlar tarkibida uchrashi bizni ana shunday fikrga kelishimizga sababchi bo'ldi. Bu haqda keyingi o'rinlarda muhokama yuritimiz.

Ilmiy fantastika ijodining o'ziga xos xususiyati uning voqealarni oldindan prognoz qilishidir. Fantastikaning negizida ehtimollik prognozi, ya'ni taraqqiy etib kelayotgan fan va texnika sohasidagi yutuqlarning ilmiy tahlili hamda inson xayoliy tafakkurining birlashib, o'ziga xos kombinatsiyasi natijasida hosil bo'lgan voqea-hodisalar yotadi. Bu jihatni biz ushbu atamaning ta'riflarida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin: «ilmiy fantastika - bu ratsional fikrga ega bo'lgan ilmiy kashfiyotlar, texnik ixtirolar yoki tabiat qonunlari yordamida asarda o'sha davrning tabiiy ilmiy qarashlariga zid bo'lib, g'ayrioddiy yoki g'ayritabiiy narsa yaratilgan» farazga asoslangan adabiyot turi. Ilmiy fantastika insonning ilmiy texnika yutuqlari asosida yaratilgan g'ayrioddiy narsalar va olm-fan yutuqlari natijasi bo'lmish fantastik loyihalarga to'la kelajak dunyo haqidagi orzu-umidlarini aks ettiradi. Uning yordami bilan inson imkonsiz narsani tasavvur eta oladi. Ilmiy fantastik asarlarda kelajakni bashorat qilish uchun kundalik voqelikni, modellarni, taxminlarni, tajribalarni amalga oshiriladi. Bu ilmiy-fantastik asarlarning kitobxonlar orasida ommabopligini belgilaydi.

A. Vozdvijenskaya ilmiy fantastikaning kelib chiqishini sarguzasht adabiyotidan topib, u "eng boshidan beri so'zning tom ma'nodagi sarguzashtdan fikr va ruh sarguzashtlarigacha bo'lgan sarguzasht yo'nalishi bilan ajralib turardi". T.A. Chernishev, o'z navbatida, detektiv hikoya va ilmiy fantastikani o'zaro bog'laydi: syujetni sirni hal qilish yo'lidagi harakatlari ilmiy fantastikaga aynan detektiv hikoyadan kelgan.

Shuni ta'kidlab o'tamizki, fantastika ildizlari qadim zamonlarda - mifologiya, ertak, afsonalar, keyinchalik - gotika romani, sarguzasht romani va umuman olganda romantizmga bog'liq. Fantastika va ertaklar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni E.M. Neyolov quyidagicha tasvirlab beradi: tadqiqotchi folklor va ertaklarni o'ziga xos tarzda aniqlaydi: ilmiy fantastikaga xos bo'lgan tuzilmalarning tabiati: vaqtni boshqarish; kosmik boshqaruv; ajoyib hikoya tuzilishi (yo'lning sehrli-ertak obrazi bilan belgilanadi), "odam (qabila) - tabiat" qarama-qarshiligi, "o'zniki" - "begona" va boshqalar. Bizning fikrimizcha, E.M. Neyolovning fantastika va ertaklar o'rtasidagi genetik bog'liqlik haqidagi xulosalari fantastik yo'nalishdagi asarlarga to'liq qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Fentezi badiiy adabiyotning o'ziga xos yo'nalishi bo'lib, unda real, fantastik, subreal, mistik chegaralar xiralashadi va syujet irratsional xarakterdagi taxminlarga asoslanadi. Bu tahmin matnda mantiqiy asosga ega emas, u ilmiy fantastikadan farqli o'laroq, oqilona tushuntirib bo'lmaydigan faktlar va hodisalar mavjudligini taxmin qiladi. E'tibor bering, J. R.

Tolkin o'z asarlarini sehrli ertaklar deb atagan. Ilmiy adabiyotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, fentezi mualliflarining vazifalari o'zlarining iloji boricha haqiqiy va ishonchli bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan virtual dunyosini yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Shunday qilib, fantastika va fentezi sohalarini farqlash uchun biz E.N. Kovtunning fikriga murojaat qilishimiz mumkin: ya'ni, hozirda haqiqatda kuzatilmaydigan (lekin kelajakda yoki prinsipial jihatdan unda paydo bo'lishi mumkin) holatlar bilan ilmiy fantastika shug'ullanadi. Dunyo haqidagi zamonaviy ilmiy g'oyalar nuqtayi nazaridan, "mutlaqo mavjud bo'lmaydigan" narsa fentezidir [14].

Fantastika janrining aksariyat tadqiqotchilari fentezining asosiy g'oyaviy-estetik tamoyillarining shakllanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatgan manbalar deb mif, qahramonlik eposi, ertak, rivoyatlar, ritsarlik romantikasi, sarguzasht romani, gotika romanlarini hisoblashadi. Fentezining afsonalar bilan genetik aloqasi ko'rsatilgan va bu borada ko'plab adabiyotshunos olimlar ishlagan: "Xayol olami - bu zamonaviy ongdan o'tgan va muallifning irodasi bilan qayta tiklangan qadimiy miflar, afsonalar, ertaklardir".

Adabiyotshunos olim A.M.Prixodkoning ta'kidlashicha, afsona metaforik - utopik tafakkurning eng yorqin ko'rinishi bo'lib, "haqiqatning chuqur tuzilmalarini" mifologik asosda ochib berish" va "kundalik voqelikdan ajratilgan va uzoqlashtirilgan janr" fentezi asosida yotadi. Shunday qilib, "u yoki bu qadimiy mifologik tizimning qonunlariga qat'iy rioya qilish yoki muallif tomonidan yaratilgan o'ziga xos afsonasi bu janrning tuzilishini belgilaydi".

O.P.Krinitina fentezi turlari mifologik mavzularga, xudolar panteoniga, an'analarga, afsonalarga va kundalik voqelikka bog'liq deb hisoblaydi. Fentezida taqdim etilgan dunyo modeli mifologik tafakkurning yaxshilik va yomonlikni shaxsiylashtirish, tabiiy hodisalarni insoniylashtirish, mikrokosmos va makrokosmosni aniqlash, fazo-vaqt sinkretizmi, binar mantiq kabi xususiyatlarini ochib beradi.

A.M.Prixodko fentezining tabiati haqida fikr yuritar ekan, bu janrdagi adabiyot mif yaratish jarayoni - utopik tafakkur bilan bog'liq jarayonning aksi ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. Fantastik adabiyotning barcha mualliflari allaqachon ma'lum bo'lgan an'anaviy mifologik tizimlarga murojaat qiladigan va o'zlarining dunyoning mifologik konsepsiyasi asl nusxalarini yaratadigan mif yaratadilar. A.M.Prixodko ta'kidlaganidek, asar ma'lum formula yoki sxemaga asoslangan bo'lib, u qahramonlarning syujet harakatlari va harakatlarining ma'lum bir taxminiyligi, personajlarda psixologizmning yo'qligi va boshqalarda namoyon bo'ladi. Fentezi asari "...ma'lum bir shakli, individual muallif dizaynlari qatlamlangan matritsani o'z ichiga oladi".

Fentezi yo'nalishidagi asarlarda ilmiy tafakkur bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan va ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyot yutuqlarini o'zida aks ettirmaydigan o'ziga xos, muallifning mifologik modeli yaratiladi. Biroq shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, quyi fentezi yo'nalishidagi ayrim asarlarda olmiy fantastikaga xos xususiyatlar ham ruzatiladi. Bu haqda keying boblarda muhokama yuritimiz.

Fentezining asosiy tarkibiy qismlari xudolar, olijanob qahramonlar va afsonaviy hayvonlar kabi arxetip obrazlar bo'lib, yaxshilik va yovuzlik kuchlari o'rtasida majburiy va doimiy kurash jarayoni kechadigan sehr-joduga to'la ajoyib hayoliy dunyo uning asosiy makonidir.

Bir qator tadqiqotchilar fantastika (shuningdek, yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, ilmiy fantastika) sarguzasht adabiyoti bilan bog'liqligini ta'kidlashadi. Fentezi yo'nalishidagi asarlar o'zida mif, ertak va sarguzasht adabiyoti elementlarini mujassam etadi. Fentezi, albatta, o'zidan oldingi adabiy yo'nalishlarning ayrim xususiyatlari va qonuniyatlarini o'zlashtirgan xolda adabiy yo'nalish sifatida maydonga keldi. Romantizmdan fenteziga g'ayrioddiy vaziyatlar,

shartlar va xarakterlar o'tgan bo'lsa, realizmdan esa - psixologik haqiqiylikka intilish, "g'ayrioddiy narsalarga qiziqish" kabi adabiy unsurlar o'tgan.

A.Vozdvijenskaya XX asrning ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab ilmiy-fantastik asarlar paydo bo'la boshlaganini ta'kidlaydi, bu erda "detektiv yo'nalish fundamental bo'lib, odatiy ilmiy-fantastik, atributlarning detektiv janri: aqlli detektiv, uquvsiz politsiyachi, mashaqqatli dalillar to'plash kabi to'liq to'plami mavjud. Ba'zan sirli qotillik, g'oyib bo'lish yoki o'g'irlik faqat harakatning qolgan qismini rivojlanishiga turtki beradi".

Sarguzashtli (detektiv) ilmiy-fantastik adabiyotning xususiyatlari, A. Vozdvijenskayaning fikricha, quyidagilardir:

- syujetni rivojlantirishning detektiv prinsipi - topishmoqlardan sirlar va sarguzashtlar orqali hal qilishgacha;
- ekstremal vaziyatlarga tushib qolgan va o'lim xavfi yoqasida turgan qahramonlar;
- yovuz odam bilan jang qilish;
- dinamik harakat, to'satdan syujet burilishlari (sirlar, ta'qiblar, qotilliklar, otishmalar va boshqalar).

R.A.Balashova ilmiy fantastika janrning turlarini quyidagicha aniqlaydi: ilmiy-fantastik sayohat romani, ilmiy-fantastik satirik va yumoristik roman, ilmiy-fantastik sarguzasht romani, jangovar, triller, detektiv hikoya.

Ilmiy-fantastik romanda ko'pincha qahramon yolg'iz harakat qiladi, qarama-qarshi dunyo va biz hikoya qilish jarayonida uning shakllanishini kuzatamiz. Qahramonning atrofdagi dunyodan begonalashuvi holatlari kuzatiladi, uning ma'naviy sargardonligi muallif ongi orqali yetkaziladi", bu ilmiy fantastikaning asosiy motivlaridan biridir. Fantastik adabiyotning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari (ilmiy fantastika va fantastika) va izquvar romanni birlashtirgan fantastik josuslik romani ushbu yondashuv doirasida juda mos keladi. shunday qilib, ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish, umuman olganda, fantastik adabiyotning asosiy xususiyatlarini aniqlash imkonini berdi:

- fantastika va fentezining genetik ildizlari - mif, ertak, sarguzasht adabiyoti;
- fantastikada dunyo va insonni ilmiy tushunishga asoslanadigan, fentezida matnda mantiqiy motivga ega bo'lmagan faraz tamoyili; ratsional (ilmiy) izohlab bo'lmaydigan fakt va hodisalarning mavjudligi tahmin qilinadi;
- real dunyoga parallel ravishda xayoliy, simulyatsiya qilingan, subreal dunyoni yaratishni o'z ichiga olgan modellashtirish prinsipi. Bu olamlar bir-birining ustiga qurilishi, qarama-qarshi qo'yilishi, solishtirilishi, turli proporsional munosabatlarda bo'lishi va hokazo;
- qochish tamoyili;
- "real - noreal" qarama-qarshiligi;
- umumiy madaniy "o'ziniki - boshqasiniki" qarama-qarshilik;
- "formulaviy tabiat" (formula yoki sxemaga asoslanadi; har qanday ish ma'lum qoidalarga muvofiq quriladi);
- g'ayritabiiy yoki g'ayrioddiy narsalarga asoslangan qahramonni aniqlash;
- tasvirning fantastik turi (an'anaviylik, mantiqiy aloqalar va qoidalarning buzilishi, tasvirlangan ob'ektning nisbati va shakllari);
- yozuvchining ham, o'quvchining ham ijodiy g'oyalari va fantaziyalarining to'planishi.

Sehrli realizm tushunchasi kundalik hayotga afsona va haqiqatga mos kelmaydigan xayolot maxsulini qo'shish orqali bunyod etilgan badiiy ijod namunasiga nisbatan qo'llaniladi.

Ma'lum bir asarni sehrli realizm uslubida yozilishining o'ziga xos shart-sharoitlari mavjud bo'lib, ular quyidagilardan iborat:

1. Mantiqiy qonuniyatni inkor etuvchi voqealarning mavjudligi. Masalan, Frans Kafkaning “Evrilish” asarida bosh qahramon Gregor bir kechada qo‘ng‘izga aylanib qoladi. Xudoyberdi To‘xtaboyevning “Sariq devni minib” asarida bosh qahramon sehrli qalpoqcha topib oladi. Eng muhim joyi shundaki, bu har ikki voqea 20-asrda ro‘y beradi. Odamning qo‘ng‘izga aylanishi va sehrli qalpoqchanning mavjud ekani hozirgi davr mantiqiy qonuniyatini inkor etuvchi hodisalardir.

2. Mif va afsonalarning mavjud bo‘lishi.

3. Tarixiy konteks va ijtimoiy muammolarning mavjud bo‘lishi.

4. Vaqt va voqealar ketma-ketligining buzilishi.

5. Real borliq va atrof-muhitning mavjudligi. Sehrli realizm yo‘nalishida yozilgan asarlarda voqea-hodisalar o‘zga sayyoralar yoki sehrli olamlarda ro‘y bermaydi. Bunday asarlarda oddiy, kundalik hayot tasvirlanadi. Bunday asarlardagi personajlar ham real odamlardir.

6. Jiddiylik. Sehrli realizmning eng muhim xususiyatlaridan biri bu undagi bayon uslubining har qanday ehtirosiz, oddiy ekanida. Har qanday g‘alati voqea-hodisalar ham oddiygina hikoya qilinadi.

Biroq shuni alohida ta’kidlash lozimki, sehrli realizm uslubida yozilgan asarlar tipologiyasi bo‘yicha yuqorida keltirilgan tasniflarda xali hanuz mukammallik kuzatilmaydi. Zero, syujet liniyasiga sehr va g‘ayritabiiylik aralashgan, qorishiq tarzda realizm asarlar shunchalik turfa xilki, ularni ma’lum bir xususiyatlariga ko‘ra tasniflash xali ancha tadqiqotlar o‘tkazish va xulosalar olishni taqazo etadi.

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THE CAMPUS NOVEL AND ITS DISTINCTIVE FEATURES IN MODERN LITERATURE

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Abstract: The campus novel is a well-known type of modern story. It uses the college setting to look at society and to think about ideas of right and wrong. This piece looks at what makes a campus novel what it is, including where it came from, what it is about, and how the stories are told.

Key words: campus novel, academic fiction, satire, modern literature, university life.

The campus novel, or academic novel, is a genre that focuses on life in universities and colleges. It became popular in the mid-20th century and has become a way to comment on society. It gives us an inside look at the intellectual and social happenings of university life while also pointing out the hypocrisies of academic culture. Before this genre, literature included scholars and students, but the real campus novel started after World War II, especially in Britain and the United States. This was when higher education became key to getting ahead in society and forming a cultural identity. Writers like Kingsley Amis, David Lodge, Malcolm Bradbury, and Philip Roth helped define the genre. They always used satire, ambition, and intellectual letdown as themes.

One key thing about the campus novel is its limited setting. The university is like a small world that shows the hierarchies and conflicts of the larger world. In this setting, characters fight over things like tenure and reputation. The university becomes a stage to look at human flaws and ambition, often representing bigger social issues. Another key is satire. Writers use irony and humor to show the pretensions and contradictions of the academic world. For example, in *Lucky Jim*, Amis makes fun of the self-importance of British academics. In David Lodge's *Changing Places* (1975), the university is where different cultures meet and misunderstand each other. The humor entertains and calls out the difference between intellectual beliefs and personal flaws. These novels usually focus on the moral problems of the main characters. Professors and students deal with questions about being real, being ambitious, and what education means. These struggles show bigger cultural arguments about truth, authority, and identity. Through these issues, the campus novel comments on both philosophy and society. Many of these novels discuss class, gender, and power in institutions.

In Mary McCarthy's *The Groves of Academe*, female and minority academics face biases in the system. Later works, like Zadie Smith's *On Beauty* (2005), talk about race, globalization, and postcolonial identity. The genre changes with society and uses the university to look at cultural and political changes. The campus novel often uses literary theory and academic terms in its story. This makes it hard to tell the difference between fiction

and criticism. It lets the novel talk about how it was created and about intellectual conversation. In doing so, it gets the often-strange parts of academic life. Recently, the campus novel has gone beyond just Western universities. Writers around the world have used the genre to show academic institutions in Asia, Africa, and Eastern Europe as places of corruption and resistance. These newer works show how education systems struggle with economic pressures and globalization. No matter these changes, the main draw of the campus novel is still there: it can show the human side of intellectual life while looking closely at its issues. The campus novel is unique in modern literature because it's a social satire and an intellectual search. Its confined setting, satire, moral conflict, and focus on institutions allow it to capture how tricky university life can be. It's not just fiction about professors and students. The campus novel shows lasting questions about power and the search for truth. As higher education changes, the campus novel is still a key way to look at the connection between intellect, identity, and society.

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SHAXMATNING ZAMONAVIY ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolamizda biz shaxmat va adabiyot o'rtasida juda ko'p umumiy tomonlar uyg'unligini yoritib bermoqchimiz, O'zbekistonning buyuk shoir va adabiyotchilarimizning qalamlariga mansub bo'lgan she'rlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Shaxmat, she'riyat, barkamol avlod, debyut, mitelshpil, endishpils, adabiyotchilar, tugun, kulminatsiya

Аннотация: В этой статье мы хотим пролить свет на то, что между шахматами и литературой существует много общего, представлены стихи великих поэтов и литераторов Узбекистана, которые принадлежат их Перу. **Ключевые слова:** шахматы, поэзия, идеальное поколение, дебют, мительшпиль, эндишпиль, литераторы, узел, кульминация

Annotation: in this article we want to highlight the harmony of many common sides between chess and literature, the poems of Uzbekistan, which belong to the Pencils of our great poets and literati.

Keywords: Chess, poetry, harmonious generation, debut, mitelshpil, endishpils, literati, knot, climax

Mamlakatimizda bunyodkorlik jarayoni amalga oshayotgan hozirgi paytda ma'naviy-axloqiy etuk, intellektual rivojlangan, jismonan baquvvat, o'tkir zehnliligi, har tomonlama kamol topgan shaxsni shakllantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Jumladan, muhtaram Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoev o'z ma'ruzalarida: Buyuk tarixda hech narsa izsiz ketmaydi. U xalqlarning qonida, tarixiy xotirasida saqlanadi va amaliy ishlarida namoyon bo'ladi. Shuning uchun ham u qudratlidir. Tarixiy merosni asrab-avaylash, o'rganish va avlodlardan avlodlarga qoldirish davlatimiz siyosatining eng muhim ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biridir, [1. 29- b.] deb ta'kidlaganlar.

Quyida, xalqimiz suygan shoirlar Erkin Vohidov, Abdulla Oripov, iste'dodli yozuvchi O'tkir Hoshimov va Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universitetining professor o'qituvchilari benazir va ardoqli ustozlar O.Tog'aev, I. Qo'chqortoev, J.Musaev, A.Qayumov, U.Normatov, B.Qosimov, S.Umirov, T.Dalimov, Azimboy Sa'dullaev, Anatoliy Sa'dullaev, R. Inog'omov, akademik S.Sirojiddinov, Y.To'raqulov, O. Sodiqov, T.Azlarov, T.Sarimsoqov, M.Salohiddinov, A.Abduazizov, Sh.Rahmatullaev, T.Sirliboev, K.Muqimov, N.Ibragimov, T.Ernazarov, taniqli yozuvchi X. Do'stmuhammad ishtirokidagi o'yinlar chog'ida tarixiy mahorabalar, badiiy asarlarning yorqin syujetlari katakka ko'chib, bamisoli o'tmish jonlangan. Bu esa shu atrofda yig'ilgan yoshlar, ayniqsa, talabalar uchun o'ziga xos saboq, yosh shaxmatchilar uchun mahorat darsiga aylanib ketgan. [5. 23- b.]

Mazkur universitetning faxriy bitiruvchisi- O'zbekiston xalq shoiri Erkin Vohidovning shaxmatga bag'ishlangan "She'r va shaxmat" she'ri ham o'sha qizg'in va samimiy kechgan shaxmat uchrashuvlarida tug'ilgan. Mana, qalbimizga yaqin bo'lgan o'sha, mashhur satrlar:

Katak qog'ozdagi to'rt yo'l she'r kabi

Shaxmat donalari saf chekkan qator.

Nayzador fili-u shoh suvoraspi,

Tug'bardor farzini hujumga tayyor.

Shaxmatni she'r bilan qiyosyladim,

Bilimdon o'quvchim, qilma e'tiroz.

She'r axir emasmi, shaxmatdek qadim,

Shaxmatda yo'qmi yo she'riy ehtiros. [2. 5-9- b.]

Har holda shaxmat va adabiyot o'rtasida juda ko'p umumiy tomonlar bor.

Quyida mana shunaqa xos tomonlardan bir qanchasini misol keltiraman:

1. Shaxmat o'yinidan oladigan barcha qanoat va zavq xuddi musiqa yoki qiziq she'r tinglagandagi zavq bilan teng keladi. O'yinimizdagi xatolarimiz esa kompozitor yoki shoirning xatolarini eslatadi.

2. Poeziyadagi kabi shaxmatda ham eng muhim narsa ritm, o'lchovidir. Shaxmatdagi barcha donalar juft-juftidir. She'rda buni qofiya deyiladi. Bunday qofiyalanishni o'zbekchada musamman usuli deb ataladi.

3. She'rning jon joyi bo'ladi, shaxmatni ham hal qiluvchi bitta yurish uchun o'ynaladi. Hikoyada kutilmagan yakun, shaxmatda esa-kutilmagan yurish qadrlanadi.

4. Xonasini topib qilish shaxmatchilardagina emas, balki adabiyotchilarda ham border.

5. Siz: debyut, mitelshpil, endishplis desangiz, adabiyotchilar: tugun, kulminatsiya, yechim, final deydi.

6. Seytnotga tushmagan yozuvchi bo'lmasa kerak. Hayot kishini doimo shoshirgani-shoshirgan. Shaxmatda esa har bir daqiqa qimmatlidir.

7. Hayotdagi qarama- qarshiliklarni badiiy adabiyotda tasvirlash konflikt deyiladi. Bir o'ylab ko'ringa shaxmat ham xuddi yaxshi drama asari singari konfliktga asoslangan emasmi? Konfliktsizlik nazariyasi shaxmatga yot. Darvoqe, u adabiyotga ham bo'lmasligi kerak.

8. Shaxmat ham odamlar, ularning qo'shiqlari, ijodlari singari qadimiydir. Biroq mana shu qadimiy tarix mobaynida shaxmatchilar ham, shoirlar ham doimo shohlarga hujum

qilib kelishgan. To'g'ri, bu hujum badiiy obrazda yoki shaxmat donasida in'ikos etilgan hayotiy voqelikning simvolik hujumidir.

9. Piyodalarning o'yin davomida farzinga chiqishini ko'ra turib, mening hayqirgim keladi:

10. Yoshlar tirishavering! Maqsad sari dadil intiluvchi bo'ling! General bo'lishni orzu qilmaydigan askar yomon askardir! Pushkin ham gimnazist edi. Alisher esa Navoiy bo'lib tug'ilmagan.

11. Shaxmat taxtasidagi 64 ta xona behisob kombinatsiya uchun imkoniyat beradi. Bu kabi cheksiz imkoniyat shaxmat va ijod uchun umumiy xislatdir. Adabiyotda biz o'tmishning eng yaxshi an'alarini davom ettiramiz, deymiz. Shaxmatda ham shunday: Karokaning himoyasini, yana bir talay narsalarni bilmay turib, ulardan ilgariga o'tib bo'lmaydi.

12. Do'stim hatto bolalarcha motni ham inson uzoq muddat mobaynida kashf etgan. Sen bu sodda o'yinni bilib, tezroq undan oshib ketgin, deb uni yaratgan.

13. San'at qurbonsiz bo'lmaydi. Shaxmat ham shunday. Ammo qurbon berishni bilmoq kerak. Nodonlar qurbon berib yutqizadilar, donolar esa, qurbon bera turib ham yutadilar.

14. Shaxmatning tomoshabopligini men kino yoki teleko'rsatuv bilan taqqoslayman. Adabiyotdan farqli o'laroq, shaxmat tarjima talab qilmaydi. Shaxmat ham xuddi qo'shiqlar kabi har qanaqa chegaralarni beruxsat oshib, yangi-yangi dillarni zabt etaveradi. [3. 66- b.]

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytib o'tish kerakki, shaxmat haqida ko'p gapirishimiz mumkin. Lekin uni bir bora o'ynamagan, his qilmagan kishi uchun bu gaplar ahamiyatsizdek. Bu sport turiga kirishib ketish qiyin, kirishib ketgandan keyin chiqib ketish undan-da qiyin. G'alabaga bo'lgan ishtiyoq odamni yana va yana shaxmat taxtasi hamda oq va qora donalar sari yetaklayveradi. Shaxmat o'yinlarida nafaqat sport va san'at, balki falsafa, mantiq, hisob ilmlari ham o'zaro jamlanib, ajib uyg'unlik kasb etishini ta'kidlash joiz. Davomli mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi aqliy o'yinlar ichida eng asosiysi va murakkabi, mukammali bo'lgan shaxmat bilan bugungi kunda dunyoda 800 milliondan ortiq kishi shug'ullanayotgani ham bejiz emas, albatta.

Shaxmatda inson qalbidan qaynab chiqqan tuyg'ular, to'g'risidagi masala inson madaniyati tarixidan qiziqarli o'rin olgan. Eng muhim xulosa shuki, shaxmat - jahon xalqlari jamoaviy ijodining mevasi bo'lib, bunda o'rta osiyoliklarning xizmati alohida o'rin tutishi endilikda har taraflama e'tirof etilmoqda. Shaxmat insonda aqliy musobaqalarning qiziqarliroq shakllariga ehtiyoj tug'ilishi oqibatida paydo bo'lgan desak, yanglishmaymiz.

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ZAMONAVIY LINGVISTIKA TARAQQIYOTI: KOGNITIV VA RAQAMLI YO‘NALISHLAR SINTEZI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy lingvistikaning eng muhim ikki yo‘nalishi - kognitiv va raqamli (kompyuter) lingvistikalar o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqadorlik va ularning zamonaviy tilshunoslikdagi o‘rni tahlil qilinadi. Til va tafakkur munosabatini o‘rganuvchi kognitiv lingvistika bilan sun‘iy intellekt asosida matn va nutqni qayta ishlashga qaratilgan kompyuter lingvistika bir-birini to‘ldiruvchi tizimlar sifatida qaraladi. Maqolada shuningdek, tilshunoslikning raqamli davrda tutgan yangi o‘rni, avtomatik tarjima, semantik tahlil va sun‘iy intellekt texnologiyalari bilan bog‘liq muammolar ham ilmiy nuqtai nazardan yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: kognitiv lingvistika, raqamli lingvistika, sun‘iy intellekt, semantika, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash, ma’lumotlar tahlili, antropotsentrizm.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается взаимосвязь двух важнейших направлений современной лингвистики - когнитивной и цифровой (компьютерной) лингвистики, а также их роль в современном языкознании. Когнитивная лингвистика, изучающая соотношение языка и мышления, и компьютерная лингвистика, ориентированная на обработку текста и речи на основе искусственного интеллекта, рассматриваются как взаимодополняющие системы. В статье также освещается новая роль языкознания в цифровую эпоху, проблемы автоматического перевода, семантического анализа и технологий искусственного интеллекта с научной точки зрения.

Ключевые слова: когнитивная лингвистика, цифровая лингвистика, искусственный интеллект, семантика, обработка естественного языка, анализ данных, антропоцентризм.

Abstract: This article examines the interrelation between two major branches of modern linguistics - cognitive and digital (computational) linguistics - and their roles in contemporary language studies. Cognitive linguistics, which explores the relationship between language and thought, and computational linguistics, which focuses on text and speech processing based on artificial intelligence, are viewed as complementary systems. The article also discusses the new role of linguistics in the digital age, as well as scientific perspectives on challenges related to machine translation, semantic analysis, and artificial intelligence technologies.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, digital linguistics, artificial intelligence, semantics, natural language processing, data analysis, anthropocentrism.

XX asrning ikkinchi yarmida lingvistika yangi bosqichga ko‘tarildi - til endi faqat kommunikatsiya vositasi emas, balki inson tafakkurining modellashtirilgan shakli sifatida

talqin qilina boshlandi. Shu bilan birga, raqamli texnologiyalar taraqqiyoti tilshunoslikning yangi shaklini - kompyuter lingvistikasini yuzaga keltirdi. Bugungi kunda kognitiv yondashuv insonning bilim tuzilmasini ochib bersa, kompyuter yondashuvi bu bilimni texnik modelga aylantirish imkonini beradi. Shunday qilib, zamonaviy lingvistika o'z rivojida "inson va mashina tafakkuri"ni birlashtiruvchi fan sifatida shakllanmoqda.

Kognitiv lingvistika - bu inson tafakkuri va til o'rtasidagi murakkab aloqani o'rganadigan fan sohasi. Uning markazida semantika va konseptual tahlil turadi. Til birliklari inson ongidagi bilim modellarini aks ettiradi. Masalan, "olam manzarasi" (lingvokognitiv model) tushunchasi orqali til har bir xalqning mental dunyoqarashini qanday shakllantirishini ochib beradi. Kognitiv lingvistikada asosiy yo'nalishlar quyidagilar: Freym nazariyasi (Ch. Fillmor), Metafora nazariyasi (G. Lakoff, M. Jonson) va Konseptual integratsiya nazariyalari. Bu yo'nalishlar tilni nafaqat tuzilma sifatida, balki fikrlash mexanizmining ifodasi sifatida o'rganishga xizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, kognitiv lingvistika antropotsentrik paradigmaga asoslanadi, ya'ni inson tafakkuri, tajribasi va madaniy dunyoqarashi markazga olinadi. Tilni tushunish uchun uni inson tafakkuri bilan birga o'rganish zarur, chunki til nafaqat voqelikni ifodalaydi, balki uni yaratadi. Shu bois, kognitiv lingvistika nafaqat lingvistik, balki falsafiy, psixologik va madaniy yondashuvlarni ham birlashtiradi.

Kompyuter lingvistika - bu lingvistik muammolarni algoritmik va dasturiy vositalar yordamida hal qiluvchi fan yo'nalishi. Uning rivojlanishi 1950-yillarda avtomatik tarjima tizimlarining yaratilishi bilan boshlandi. Bugungi kunda kompyuter lingvistikasi tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash (Natural Language Processing - NLP), korpus lingvistika, semantik tarmoqlar va sun'iy intellekt asosida matn tahlili kabi yo'nalishlarni qamrab oladi.

Kompyuter lingvistikasining amaliy ahamiyati juda keng: avtomatik tarjima, matn tahrirlash, nutqni tanish, ovozli yordamchilar, va hatto tilni o'rganish dasturlari aynan shu sohaga asoslanadi. Shuningdek, kompyuter lingvistika katta ma'lumotlar (Big Data) asosida til birliklarining chastotasini, semantik bog'lanishlarini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Bu yondashuv tilshunoslikni raqamli tahlil darajasiga olib chiqadi.

So'nggi yillarda kognitiv va kompyuter lingvistikalar bir-birini to'ldirib, integratsion paradigma sifatida shakllandi. Kognitiv lingvistika inson ongining ichki tuzilishini ochib bersa, kompyuter lingvistika uni tashqi - raqamli shaklda qayta yaratadi. Bu sintez natijasida tilning yangi texnologik modellarini yaratish mumkin bo'ldi. Masalan, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ChatGPT, DeepL, Google Translate kabi tizimlar semantik tahlil va kognitiv modellarni uyg'unlashtirgan holda ishlaydi.

Kognitiv va raqamli yondashuvning birlashuvi nafaqat lingvistik nazariyani, balki inson tafakkurini chuqurroq anglashni ham ta'minlaydi. Shuningdek, bu yondashuv tilni o'rganishda yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi - masalan, mashinaviy tarjimada kontekstual moslikni aniqlash, nutqdagi emotsional holatni tahlil qilish va til o'zgarishlarini kuzatish imkonini beradi.

Sun'iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalari lingvistik tadqiqotlarni yangi bosqichga olib chiqdi. AI asosidagi tizimlar matn va nutqni chuqur semantik tahlil qilish, avtomatik tarjima, til o'rganish va muloqotni avtomatlashtirish imkonini beradi. Bundan tashqari, tarixiy manbalarni raqamlashtirish, qadimiy yozuvlarni o'qish va ularni zamonaviy til bilan solishtirish jarayonlari ham AI orqali amalga oshirilmoqda.

Bugungi kunda lingvistika sun'iy intellekt yordamida nafaqat tahliliy, balki prognostik fan sifatida rivojlanmoqda. Ya'ni til tizimidagi o'zgarishlarni oldindan taxmin qilish, yangi leksik birliklarning paydo bo'lishini kuzatish va ularning semantik rolini baholash mumkin bo'lmoqda.

Zamonaviy lingvistika inson tafakkurini anglash, uni modellashtirish va texnik tizimlarda qayta yaratish darajasiga etgan fan sohasidir. Bugungi kunda tilshunoslik nafaqat nutq va til birliklarini o'rganadi, balki ularning kognitiv, psixologik va sotsial jarayonlar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligini ham chuqur tahlil qiladi. Ayniqsa, kognitiv va raqamli lingvistikalar sintezi natijasida inson tafakkurining raqamli modellarini yaratish imkoniyati paydo bo'ldi. Bu esa til faoliyatining texnologik ifodasini ta'minlaydi.

Kognitiv yondashuv tilni inson tafakkurining in'ikoschisi sifatida tahlil qilsa, raqamli yondashuv bu bilimlarni algoritmik tizimlarga joylashtirish imkonini beradi. Natijada til o'rganish, avtomatik tarjima, nutq tahlili, ma'no aniqlash va sun'iy intellekt asosida muloqot tizimlarini yaratish singari jarayonlar yanada mukammal darajaga chiqdi. Shuningdek, lingvistika hozirda ilmiy tahlilning yangi bosqichiga ko'tarilib, tabiiy fanlar bilan ham integratsiyalashmoqda.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikning bu bosqichi ijtimoiy hayotning turli jabhalarida ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Masalan, til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi munosabat, insonning emotsional holatini tilda ifodalash, til o'zgarishlarini statistik tahlil qilish, milliy mentalitetning lingvistik ifodalarini aniqlash singari yo'nalishlar fanlararo tadqiqotlar uchun muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, raqamli texnologiyalar orqali til materiallarini saqlash, qayta ishlash va tahlil qilish imkoniyatlari lingvistik tadqiqotlarga yangi ufqlar ochmoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, zamonaviy lingvistika bugungi raqamli asrning eng dinamik va istiqbolli fanlaridan biridir. Kognitiv va kompyuter yondashuvlarning uyg'unlashuvi tilshunoslikni yangi sifat bosqichiga olib chiqdi. Bu jarayon nafaqat ilmiy izlanishlar uchun, balki ta'lim, tarjima, kommunikatsiya, axborot texnologiyalari va madaniyatshunoslik uchun ham beqiyos imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Shu sababli, kelajak lingvistikasi inson tafakkuri bilan sun'iy intellektni birlashtiruvchi universal bilim sohasi sifatida shakllanib bormoqda.

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SEMANTIC FIELDS IN U.S. OIKONYMY: GEOGRAPHY, RELIGION, AND COMMEMORATION

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Annotation. This article explores the semantic fields that shape the naming of inhabited places (oikonyms) in the United States, focusing on three dominant categories: geography, religion, and commemoration. The study examines how each semantic field contributes to the cultural and linguistic character of U.S. place names, often overlapping and revealing layers of historical, ideological, and environmental influence. Geographic names frequently describe natural features and reflect linguistic heritage; religious names convey spiritual values and colonial missions; commemorative names preserve memory and assert cultural power. By analyzing examples across regions and historical periods, the paper demonstrates how these fields intersect and evolve.

Keywords: Toponymy, Oikonymy, Place Names, United States, Semantic Fields, Geography, Religion, Commemoration, Naming Practices, Cultural Geography.

Main text. The naming of places - in particular inhabited places or settlements (oikonyms) - in the United States provides insight into how human communities conceptualise their environment, identity and memory. In onomastics (the study of names), place-names are more than mere labels: they encode meanings, cultural values, historical contingencies and power relations. In the U.S. context, three semantic fields in particular stand out in the domain of oikonymy (and more broadly, settlement and populated-place names): (1) geography/nature (how the environment and landscape is referenced), (2) religion (how belief systems and religious heritage shape names), and (3) commemoration (how persons, events or institutions are memorialised through naming). This article explores each of these fields in turn, considers their interactions, and reflects on their implications for understanding U.S. cultural geography and naming practices.

A foundational force in naming places is the descriptive reference to physical landscapes, characteristic natural features and environmental observation. According to the general field of toponymy, many place-names are “feature names” – hydronyms, oronyms, vegetation names – that reflect the environment. [1, p. 2] For instance, the Encyclopaedia Britannica defines toponymy as concerned with the “motive behind the naming of the place (historical and geographical aspects)” and divides habitation and feature names accordingly. [2, p. 1]

In the U.S., this means that many town and settlement names derive directly from physical or topographic characteristics: e.g., “Green Valley”, “Clear Lake”, “Rocky Mount”, “Long Prairie”, and similar formations. Such names reflect the immediate landscape or what settlers observed upon arrival, thus embedding a geography-based semantic field. Moreover, the language of naming often preserves older lexical forms or indigenous words applied to natural features, which then become oikonyms or settlement names. For example, towns in Utah or the American West may retain Native American names referring to local vegetation or geology (e.g., the town of Koosharem, Utah derives from a Piute word for the valley named for deep red clover) [3].

Furthermore, the geography semantic field in U.S. oikonymy is layered with linguistic heritage: indigenous names (e.g., Mississippi, Minnesota), Spanish names (e.g., Los Angeles, Rio Grande), French names (e.g., Des Moines) and English descriptive forms (e.g.,

Pleasant Hill). The mixture reflects successive waves of settlement, colonisation and linguistic contact. In many cases the generic part of the toponym (-ville, -burg, town, city) is appended to descriptive or landscape-based specifics. For example, town names like “Clear Lake City” or “Grand Prairie Town” emphasise descriptive landscape matter. As one geography textbook shows: generic toponyms (Centre, Corners, etc.) provide clues to settlement patterns and cultural region spread [4, p. 164].

Thus, the geography/nature semantic field functions on at least three levels: (a) **descriptive naming** based on visible physical features; (b) **linguistic layering/heritage**, reflecting settlement history; (c) **heritage retention** of older or indigenous names that refer to geography.

Beyond descriptive geography, many U.S. place-names reflect religious motive, heritage or aspiration. Such names include saints’ names, biblical place names, references to Christian concepts or virtues, and denominational or church-based settlement names [5, p. 1]

In English-speaking colonial and post-colonial America, settlers often gave names such as Bethlehem, Nazareth, Zion, Providence, Salem (from Hebrew “shalom” meaning peace) to their towns in order to infuse them with a religious or utopian aspiration. [6, p. 2] In Spanish and French colony-derived regions the use of “San ...”, “Santa ...”, “St. ...” is widespread (e.g., San Antonio, Santa Fe, St. Mary’s).

Importantly, religious naming is not only functional but symbolic: it situates the new settlement within a religious worldview, signifying piety, hope or identity. Over time, the religious aura may fade, and the name becomes secularised, yet the origin remains embedded (as noted in the Washington Post piece) [5, p. 1]. The choice of biblical or saint names also reflects cultural geopolitics: for example, Catholic missionary naming in the Southwest vs. Protestant settlement naming in New England.

Thus, the religion semantic field contributes a second significant layer to U.S. oikonymy: beyond what the land is, the name reflects what the settlers hoped or believed it to be.

A third robust semantic field in U.S. place-naming is commemoration: naming places after persons, events, institutions, symbolic ideals or historical occurrences. The federal report by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) explains: “Naming ... after individuals was one way settlers marked the land... Even today, naming geographic features after individuals helps us to recognise their special achievements and contributions ...” [7, p. 1]

In settlement naming, this appears in towns or cities named after national figures (Washington, Jefferson, Madison), explorers (Hudson), local founders, or veterans. The classification of toponyms often lists “commemorative names (honours a famous or important person)” as one major category [4, p. 164]. Commemorative naming is distinct from descriptive or religious naming because it encodes memory and symbolic value: naming becomes a form of honouring, remembering, legitimising.

For example, the process of renaming the U.S. highest peak from “Mount McKinley” (named after President McKinley) back to the indigenous “Denali” reflects tensions in commemorative naming, power and heritage. The policy of the U.S. Board on Geographic Names (BGN) highlights that commemoration must satisfy criteria, and that derogatory or offensive names should be changed [3]. The BGN’s procedures make clear how institutional decisions shape commemoration through naming. Thus, the commemoration semantic field includes: (a) **honouring persons or events**, (b) **institutional naming and power**, (c) **renaming/contest-naming** (i.e., changes due to cultural shifts).

In U.S. oikonymy, the commemoration field often overlaps with geography or religion: a “St Mary’s College Town” may reference religion and person, or “Grant County” may reference a person and geography.

For example, generic toponym classification (e.g., Stewart’s classification, via textbooks) includes descriptive, commemorative, religious, manufactured, shift, etc. [4, p. 164] The interplay means that a name like “Zion Valley” might refer partly to biblical aspiration (religion) and partly to a geographic valley (nature). Or “Mount Jefferson” ties a peak (geography) to a person (commemoration).

The interaction also plays out diachronically. The first naming impulse often draws from the physical landscape (geography). As settlement matures, religious or identity-motives may guide naming. As communities stabilise, commemoration becomes more common (honouring founders, war heroes, civic figures). Over time, renaming may occur to reflect changing values-e.g., removing derogatory terms, restoring indigenous names, contesting commemorative figures. The BGN’s policy on naming and renaming underscores this [3]. Scholars of hybrid toponyms show how linguistic and cultural layering reflect intersection of geographies and settlement histories (e.g., English-Spanish hybrid names in the U.S.) [8].

Studying U.S. settlement names through semantic fields has several implications:

- **Cultural insight:** The prevalence of religious names in certain regions or commemorative names in others offers clues to settlement origin, culture and identity. As the Washington Post article noted, over 1,000 biblically-named towns exist in the U.S. [6, p. 2]
- **Linguistic contact & heritage:** The layering of indigenous, Spanish, French, English naming traditions reveals language contact and settlement history. Hybrid toponyms highlight cultural merger [8].
- **Power and memory:** Naming is a claim to the land, a way of memorialising and controlling. Commemorative naming reflects who is remembered, whose contributions matter, and whose identities are foregrounded. Renaming processes reflect evolving social values (e.g., removal of derogatory names) [3].
- **Semantic typology for analysis:** Onomasticians can categorise names as descriptive/geographic, religious, commemorative (plus other types) and thereby study naming patterns quantitatively and qualitatively. Textbook classifications (e.g., Stewart’s categories) support this [4, p. 164]
- **Geo-temporal layering:** The naming framework helps in tracing historical layers: first nature/geography, then religious/ideological, then commemorative, then renaming. Researchers could develop corpora of U.S. place names and classify them accordingly to test hypotheses about settlement era, origin, language, culture.
- **Renaming and contestation:** Contemporary naming debates (e.g., replacing derogatory names or restoring indigenous names) illustrate active processes through which naming continues to matter politically and culturally [3].

Conclusion. In the United States, the naming of inhabited places is shaped by more than simple description: it is shaped by a triad of semantic fields-geography (nature/land), religion (belief/heritage) and commemoration (memory/honour). Geography gives the first layer of meaning by referencing the landscape; religion adds identity and aspiration; commemoration embeds memory and cultural politics. These fields overlap, evolve, and reflect the complex cultural geography of U.S. settlement. Applying semantic-field analysis to U.S. oikonymy offers rich insights for onomastics, historical geography and cultural studies. Future research might apply such typologies to large datasets of U.S. place-names to uncover patterns by era, region, language and naming motivation.

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СОЦИАЛЬНЫЙ ПСИХОЛОГИЗМ В МАЛОЙ ПРОЗЕ В. Я. ШИШКОВА: ОТ ВНУТРЕННЕГО МОНОЛОГА К ОБРАЗУ ПРИРОДЫ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена анализу социального психологизма в малой прозе В. Я. Шишкова. На материале рассказа «Ватага» и цикла «Чуйские были» рассматриваются способы соединения внутреннего мира героя с социально-историческим контекстом. Показано, как внутренний монолог, ретроспекция и метафоризация природного пространства формируют многомерный образ личности, переживающей давление эпохи. Доказывается, что природа у Шишкова выполняет не фоновую, а смыслообразующую функцию - становится «языком» эмоциональных состояний и социальной тревоги. Результаты полезны для курсов по истории русской литературы и теории литературы, а также для школьного и вузовского анализа текста.

Ключевые слова: В. Я. Шишков, малая проза, социальный психологизм, внутренний монолог, ретроспекция, пейзаж, «Ватага», «Чуйские были».

Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of social psychologism in the short prose of V. Ya. Shishkov. Based on the short story "Vataga" and the cycle "Chuisky Tales," the study explores the ways in which the author connects the inner world of the protagonist with the socio-historical context. It demonstrates how inner monologue, retrospection, and the metaphorization of natural space create a multidimensional image of a personality experiencing the pressures of the era. It is proved that nature in Shishkov's works performs not a background, but a meaning-forming function - becoming a "language" of emotional states and social anxiety. The results of the research are useful for courses in the history and theory of Russian literature, as well as for school and university text analysis.

Keywords: Shishkov, short prose, social psychologism, inner monologue, retrospection, landscape, *Vataga*, *Chuisky Tales*.

В истории русской литературы начало XX века характеризуется интенсивными поисками адекватных форм художественного осмысления человека в условиях стремительных социальных перемен. Малая проза в этот период становится лабораторией психологического анализа: компактность формы позволяет концентрировать внимание на переломных моментах биографии персонажа, а также на тонких переходах от внешнего события к внутреннему переживанию. Проза В. Я. Шишкова - показательный пример такого синтеза: личное в ней постоянно "сшито" с общим, а психология - с социальным опытом общности.

Теоретические ориентиры: психологизм и малая форма - Психологизм в русской прозе традиционно связан с раскрытием «внутреннего человека» через речь, память, аффекты, нравственный выбор. Для малой формы этот процесс усиливается: композиционная сжатость стимулирует «точечные» ситуации кризиса, когда привычные роли и социальные маски смещаются, а нерв текста выходит на поверхность. В таком фокусе индивидуальная психика выступает призмой, сквозь которую преломляются социальные давления и конфликты [4, с.72]. Малая форма у Шишкова работает как «ускоритель смыслов»: минимальное число эпизодов дает максимум напряжения между личной правдой и необходимостью жить «среди людей».

«Ватага»: личное и историческое: В «Ватаге» (одном из ключевых рассказов писателя) шишковская оптика соединяет индивидуальную судьбу с историческими тектониками. Внутренний монолог и вариации несобственно-прямой речи позволяют слышать «подземную» работу сознания - сомнение, страх, надежду, чувство ответственности за себя и «своих» [1.с.89]. Эти состояния не «частные»: они проистекают из дисгармонии времени, из утраты устойчивых социальных опор. Ретроспективные вкрапления, возвращающие героя к травматическим эпизодам прошлого, выполняют функцию психологической «подсветки» и одновременно социального диагноза: память объясняет не только характер, но и ландшафт эпохи.

Композиционно рассказ строится как серия внутренних развилок-решений. Внешний поступок героя всякий раз прорастает из внутреннего разговора с самим собой и воображаемым «собеседником» - коллективным опытом. Так формируется ключевая для Шишкова связка: «внутренний выбор - социальная необходимость». Психологический анализ не изолирует человека, а возвращает его в ткань общности, где любое «я» является и продуктом, и критиком исторического времени [3.с.149].

«Чуйские были»: природа как язык внутреннего: Цикл «Чуйские были» обнаруживает другой, но сопряженный с «Ватагой» механизм социального психологизма - метафоризацию природного пространства [2. с. 21]. Дорога как образ движения и испытания; река как метафора времени и перехода; горный ландшафт как зона преодоления и самоиспытания - эти коды работают двунаправленно. С одной стороны, они переводят внутренние состояния героев на язык зримых образов; с другой - возвращают психологию к социальному: движение по дороге равно движению в истории, по «камням» обстоятельств. Пейзаж у Шишкова «разговаривает»: его описания не декоративны, а драматургичны, они повышают «напряжение смысла», конденсируют конфликт.

Психологическая тональность цикла задается чередованием внешнего пути и внутреннего поиска. Моменты созерцания природы структурируют эмоциональную динамику текста: от тревоги - к решимости, от растерянности - к пониманию, от одиночества - к сопричастности. В результате пейзаж становится архитектоником, в котором читается и судьба героя, и скрытая карта социального давления.

Социальный психологизм малой прозы Шишкова - это органическое переплетение индивидуального опыта и исторического давления. В «Ватаге» внутренняя речь и ретроспекция превращают частную биографию в «чтение эпохи», в «Чуйских былых» пейзаж становится языком эмоционально-социальных смыслов. Малая форма обеспечивает компактность и напряженность анализа, а также особую этическую оптику: герой несет ответственность не только за поступок, но и за способ переживания времени. Перспективным видится сопоставление шишковской модели с прозой Горького, Ремизова, Пришвина, а также с современными практиками «новой малой прозы», где пейзаж и городское пространство вновь делают видимыми

социальные разломы. Методически материал пригоден для учебных курсов: он позволяет демонстрировать студентам, как приемы психологизма работают в жанровых границах и как «видеть» социальное в частном анализе текста.

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ЛИЧНОЕ ИМЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ МЕНТАЛЬНОСТИ: ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются антропонимы как отражение национальной картины мира на материале русских и узбекских народных сказок. Исследование проводится в лингвокультурологическом аспекте с использованием семантического, сопоставительного и контекстуального анализа. Особое внимание уделяется символике личных имён, их роли в передаче этнокультурных ценностей и функционировании в фольклорном тексте. Сравнительный подход позволил выявить как общие фольклорные закономерности, так и особенности именования, обусловленные религиозными, культурными и социальными факторами. Результаты исследования подтверждают, что антропонимы являются важными носителями культурной информации, формирующими уникальное этническое восприятие мира.

Ключевые слова: антропоним, лингвокультурология, народная сказка, национальная картина мира, русский фольклор, узбекский фольклор, имя собственное, этнокультура, символика имён.

Abstract: The article examines anthroponyms as a reflection of the national worldview based on Russian and Uzbek folk tales. The research is conducted within a linguoculturological framework using semantic, comparative, and contextual analysis. Special attention is given to the symbolism of personal names, their role in conveying ethnocultural values, and their functioning within the folklore text. The comparative approach made it possible to identify both common folkloric patterns and naming features determined by religious, cultural, and social factors. The findings confirm that anthroponyms serve as important carriers of cultural information, shaping a unique ethnic perception of the world.

Keywords: anthroponym, linguoculturology, folk tale, national worldview, Russian folklore, Uzbek folklore, proper name, ethnoculture, symbolism of names.

Антропонимы - это личные имена, которые выполняют не только номинативную, но и культурную функцию, отражая ценности, традиции и мировоззрение народа. Они являются важнейшим элементом этнической идентичности, так как позволяют проследить особенности менталитета, религиозных представлений и социальных установок различных этнических групп. Изучение антропонимов позволяет не только

глубже понять структуру языка, но и реконструировать элементы культурной памяти и национального самосознания.

В последние десятилетия интерес к антропонимам как к элементам языковой картины мира значительно возрос, особенно в контексте лингвокультурологии, которая изучает взаимосвязь языка и культуры. Особый интерес представляет сопоставительный анализ русских и узбекских антропонимов, поскольку эти культуры, несмотря на различия в происхождении и типе языка, имеют длительную историю взаимодействия и культурного обмена. Сравнение имён, их семантики, этимологии и культурных ассоциаций позволяет выявить общие черты и различия в национальных картинах мира русскоязычного и узбекскоязычного сообществ.

Методологической основой настоящего исследования стали принципы лингвокультурологического анализа, направленного на выявление взаимосвязи между языковыми единицами и культурными кодами. Также применялись элементы семантического, сравнительно-сопоставительного и контекстуального анализа. Источниками выступили русские народные сказки в редакции А.Н. Афанасьева, узбекские народные сказки ("O'zbek xalq ertaklari"), а также научные труды, посвящённые ономастике и культурологии.

Антропонимы в русских народных сказках: наиболее частотные имена: Иван, Марья Моревна, Василиса Премудрая. Часто используются прозвищные формы: Иван-царевич, Кощей Бессмертный, Баба-Яга. Эти имена выполняют функции идентификации, оценки, архетипизации, отражения религиозных и мифологических влияний. Имя Иван символизирует простого человека, героя, носителя народной мудрости. Василиса, как имя женского персонажа, олицетворяет красоту, мудрость и добродетель. Кощей Бессмертный и Баба-Яга являются антитезами героев, олицетворяющими зло и испытания[1,с.52].

Антропонимы в узбекских народных сказках: Типичные имена: Алпомиш, Зухра, Бойчечак, Занги бобо, Қоро қиз. Узбекские антропонимы часто обладают семантической прозрачностью: Алпомиш - имя героя, символизирующее силу и честь, Бой ота - отражает статус и богатство. Имена несут в себе отсылки к исламской культуре (Зухра - арабское имя, связанное с красотой и чистотой) и тюркским традициям. В них подчёркивается уважение к старшим, нравственные качества, родственные связи и социальная иерархия[2,с.67].

Сравнительный анализ показывает, что в обеих культурах имена выполняют идентифицирующую, символическую и культурно-трансляционную функцию. Однако русские имена более условны, мифологизированы, лишены прямого значения. Узбекские имена, напротив, реалистичны, прозрачны, часто описывают качества героя напрямую. Так, имя Қаро қиз (чёрная девушка) может указывать на внешность или символическую функцию персонажа. Религиозные и культурные коннотации также различны. В русском фольклоре прослеживается влияние христианства, особенно в использовании имён, происходящих от церковного канона. В узбекском - выражено исламское влияние, подчёркивающее мораль и этику, преданность и честь. Имена в обеих традициях закрепляют определённые социальные роли: цари, старцы, герои, злодеи. В сказке имя становится маркером не только личности, но и её функции в повествовании.

Антропонимы как инструмент этнической самоидентификации: Личные имена в сказках формируют этническую идентичность. Через повторяющиеся имена и мотивы народ осознаёт себя как культурное целое. Имя Иван - это не просто персонаж, это собирательный образ русского человека, как Alpomish - символ узбекского

национального героя. В результате сказка через имя транслирует ценности: храбрость, справедливость, верность. Современное значение антропонимов: интересно отметить, что многие имена из фольклора продолжают использоваться и сегодня. В Узбекистане и в России до сих пор популярны такие имена, как Зухра, Василиса, Иван, Умар, Шохрух. Это говорит о живой преемственности культурной памяти и о роли сказок как хранителей имен. Также современные медиа, мультфильмы, книги продолжают актуализировать традиционные имена, закрепляя их в массовом сознании.

Антропонимы в сказках являются важнейшими культурными элементами, транслирующими национальные ценности. В русском фольклоре имена зачастую условны и символичны, в узбекском - семантически насыщены и ориентированы на морально-нравственные ориентиры. Исследование показало, что имена в фольклоре несут функции идентификации, оценки, культурной трансляции. Перспективы дальнейших исследований включают расширение языкового материала, включение других тюркских и славянских языков, а также анализ современных имён в литературе, кино и медиа.

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“ALPOMISH” DOSTONIDAGI SHEVAGA XOS SOZLARNING LINGVISTIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada ozbek xalq epik merosining durdonasi “Alpomish” dostoni lingvistik jihatdan qisman tahlili qilinadi. Ayniqsa dostonda faol qo‘llanilgan shevaga oid sozlarning xususiyatlari, ularning fonetik, morfologik va semantik jihatlari organiladi. Tadqiqot janubiy ozbek dostonchilik maktabiga mansub variant (Umir Safar hamda Avliyo Mardonaqul) asosida olib borilgan. Maqolada sheva unsurlarining baxshi tili, og‘zaki epik uslub va milliy til taraqqiyotidagi orni yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Alpomish dostoni, baxshi tili, sheva, dialektizm, janubiy lahja, xalq tili, folklor leksikasi, qipchoq lahjasi.

Abstract: This article provides a partial linguistic analysis of the Uzbek national epic masterpiece “*Alpomish*”. Special attention is given to the dialectal words actively used in the epic, examining their phonetic, morphological, and semantic features. The study is based on the southern Uzbek epic school versions narrated by Umir Safar and Avliyo Mardonaqul. The article also explores the role of dialectal elements in the bard’s language, oral epic style, and the development of the national language.

Keywords: *Alpomish* epic, bard’s language, dialect, dialectism, southern dialect, folk language, folklore vocabulary, Kipchak dialect.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен частичный лингвистический анализ шедевра узбекского народного эпоса - «*Алпомыш*». Особое внимание уделено диалектным словам, активно использованным в эпосе, их фонетическим, морфологическим и семантическим особенностям. Исследование основано на вариантах южной узбекской эпической школы (Умир Сафар и Авлиё Мардонакул). В статье раскрывается роль диалектных элементов в языке бахши, устно-эпическом стиле и развитии национального языка.

Ключевые слова: эпос «*Алпомыш*», язык бахши, диалект, диалектизм, южный диалект, народный язык, фольклорная лексика, кыпчакский диалект.

O‘zbek xalq ogzaki ijodi tarixida “Alpomish” dostonining o‘rni beqiyosdir. U xalqning epik tafakkuri, milliy o‘zligi va ma’naviy olami, xalq tilining badiiy ifodasidir. Bu doston o‘zbek xalqining til boyligini, tarixiy leksikasini va shevalar tizimini saqlab kelayotgan tirik yodgirlikdir. “Alpomish” dostonining Fozil Yo‘ldosh o‘g‘li aytimi, Mahmud Zarifov tomonidan yozib olingan varianti xalq dostonchilik maktablarining yuksak namunasi sifatida e’tirof etiladi. Har qaysi xalqning azaliy tarixi va madaniyati, eng avvalo, uning og‘zaki ijodi – folklor san’atida, doston va eposlarida ko‘rinib, ular millatning o‘ziga xos til xususiyatlarini aks ettiradi. Shu bilan birga, xalqning milliy qadriyatlari, an’analarini rivojlantirishda bebaho manba hisoblanadi.

“Alpomish” dostonining ilmiy va badiiy qiymati uning tili boyligi bilan belgilanadi. Bu boy leksika adabiy tilning boyishidagi asosiy manbalardan biri bo‘lib, o‘zbek tili tarixiy shevalaridan biri – qipchoq dialektining lug‘at boyligini o‘zida to‘la saqlab kelmoqda. Dostonda qahramonlar xarakteri, jismoniy yetukligi yoki, nuqsonlarini ifodalashdagi xalqona tavsifni kuzatar ekanmiz, xalq tilining sifatlashlardagi til jilolariga qanchalar boy ekanligiga amin bo‘lamiz. Masalan,

Bodom bekach:

*Qaydan kelding, Qultoyqul, qaydan kelding, yoy-yoy,
Ko‘k qayg‘aday qangqillab qo‘ydan kelding, yoy-yoy.*

Qultoy:

*Hovi sening, yengajon, ravishingga, yor-yor,
Zebodayin bu mayin dovushingga, yor-yor.
Duppa-durust odamni qarg‘a deysan, yor-yor,
Ko‘k qarg‘alar uya qo‘ysin kavushingga, yor-yor.*

Bodom bekach:

*Andiyama, Qultoyqul, mandiyama, yoy-yoy,
Sakkuch degan ko‘ppakday sandiyama, yoy-yoy.
Oq changalning tubiga chiyib keldim, yoy-yoy,
Ichib olsang, chuvchining qondiyama, yoy-yoy¹.*

Aytishuvdagi qahramonlar nutqining o‘ziyoq, so‘zlayotgan shaxsning jismoniy nuqsonli (Bodom bekach) ekani, nuqsonidan orlanmasligi, o‘zgalarni pisand ilmasligini ko‘rsatish bilan birga, fe‘lidagi g‘ayirlik, suhbatdoshini kamsitishga urinish, yoqtirmaslik, g‘ashlikni ham ifodalab turibdi.

Shuningdek, dostonda ma‘nodosh sinonimlardan ham unumli foydalanilgan. Boybichaning Surxayl mastonga bergan javobida Hakimbekni bek, Alpomish, Qarchig‘ay, Qaysar, Shunqor, Zo‘rabor, Qo‘ng‘rot elining to‘rasi, Qo‘ng‘rotning bekozdi, bir yurtning vallahati kabi nomlar bilan sifatlaydi.

*Qozonda qaynagan shirboz go‘sh t emas,
To‘rda o‘tirgan qizning boshi bo‘sh emas.*

*Qizim domot bobosining uliga,
Mol bergani Boysin – Qo'ng'iroq elida.
Xabar bersa, bek Alpomish kelmaymi,
Kelsa Qorajonday o'g'ling o'lmaymi...
Qarchig'ay qarg'aga yetmik berami,
Qaysar kelsa alplar omon qolami?!²*

Shuningdek, dostonida bir qancha birliklar mavjud bo'lib xalq tilining jilosini anglash imkoni bilan birga qofiyadoshlikni ham ta'minlaydi. Jumladan, olsan-a – olsang-chi, yursan-a – yursang-chi, bo'lsan-a – bo'lsang-chi, bersan-a – bersang-chi kabi. Dostondagi olqishlar ham qipchoq lahjasi namunasi sifatida teologik tushunchalarni saqlab keladi.

Qayda borsang, Shohimardon yor bo'lsin.

O'nakimo, chilton jilovdor bo'lsin.

Dushmanlaring ko'rsa seni, zor bo'lsin.

Sen borib, salomat kelgin, bek og'a.

Men mungluqman, ko'zda selob yoshimdi(r)³.

Xalq dostonlari tilini qipchoq dialekti bilan qiyoslasak, ularning adabiy tilga munosabatini va adabiy tilni boyitishdagi ornini belgilashga harakat qilinadi. Bunda leksik-stilistik va frazeologik jihatdan ulardagi yaqinlik muhim o'rinni egallaydi. Dostondagi sozlarning deyarli barchasi talaffuzi, ma'nosi, hatto qollanilish chastotasi jihatdan qipchoq dialektiga mos kelishini tilshunos olimlarimiz ta'kidlab o'tadi. "Alpomish" dostonining tili xalq tiliga yaqindir. Unda qollanilgan: *mustor boldi-zoriqdi, munkir kelmoq gunohkor bo'lmoq, mo'r-malax- chigirtka, munshi-kotib, teva-tuya, ul-o'g'il, chovlab- ko'payib, shirxo'ra- sut ichadigan, enmoq-quyiga tushmoq, qulotuz-boshliq, g'azo-jang, g'alt urmoq-suzmoq* kabi shevaga xos sozlar xalq tilidan yozib olingan bo'lib, ular tilimizning boyligidir. "Alpomish" dostonining tili qipchoq lahjasiga mansub. Chunki, dostonni kuylagan baxshilar qipchoq vakillaridir. Buni dostonni o'rganayotganda adabiy tildan farq qiladigan fonetik, leksik, grammatik jihatlarini uchratamiz. Masalan: *y* va *j* hodisasi: *jur, jiyaman, jilayman, chechinib, chirpindi, iyyiq, bo'rboy, so'yroq, ezuv* kabi nomlanish va atashlarni uchratamiz.

Bundan tashqari qadimiy turkiy qatlamdagi so'zlar tarixiy ildizlarga ega: *alp, biy, bek, yurt, urug, boychibor*. Bu so'zlar asarda tarixiy mifologik qatlamlarni birlashtiradi. O'g'zaki epik tildagi ifodalar baxshi ijrosidagi xalqqa xos "hu boybicha", "juvonmarg", "Olloh yor", "Qo'ymay turtkilaydi", "boshini yorib qonga qorib" kabi.

"Alpomish" dostoni bugungi kun o'zbek tishunosligining rivojlanib, taraqqiy etishi uchun ham juda ko'p ilmiy, dealektal ma'lumotlar bera oladi

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. "Alpomish" dostoni. I. 38-39 bet.
2. "Alpomish: dostoni. I.54- bet.
3. "Alpomish: dostoni. I.79- bet.
4. "Alpomish: dostoni. II. 276- bet.
5. "Alpomish: dostoni. I. 192- bet.

ФЕНТЕЗИ СЕГОДНЯ ПОПУЛЯРНОСТЬ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ВЛИЯНИЕ ЖАНРА

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается феномен популярности жанра фэнтези в современной литературе и культуре. Автор анализирует его историческое развитие, ключевые особенности и влияние на мировоззрение подростков. Особое внимание уделяется произведениям Дж. Роулинг и С. Майер, ставшим символами массовой культуры. Исследуется роль фэнтези в формировании духовных и эстетических ценностей молодёжи.

Ключевые слова: фэнтези, молодёжная литература, современная культура, влияние, развитие жанра.

С самого детства я люблю читать сказки. Мне нравилось мечтать, фантазировать, погружаться в мир волшебства и приключений. Это приносило мне массу удовольствия, но я выросла, и сказки были заменены чудесным жанром фэнтези. Помимо захватывающего сюжета, который богат приключениями и волшебством, произведения в жанре фэнтези всегда имеют философский подтекст, будят воображение[1].

Жанр фэнтези сложился в литературе в прошлом веке, но свое начало берет с древних времен и очень тесно связан с культурными традициями, обычаями народов, которые нашли отражение в мифах, преданиях, сказках. Считается, что предыстория этого жанра началась с рыцарских романов эпохи Средневековья. Их действие разворачивалось в историческом времени, но происходят они на условном "феерическом" пространстве, где настоящая, подлинная география, временное пространство, границы не важны. Обычно это было некое королевство, где рыцари силой, смелостью, смекалкой противостоят колдунам и чародеям, чудовищам, великанам. В рыцарских романах стали зарождаться шаблоны, традиции современного фэнтези. В них впервые появляется образ идеального Светлого Королевства, ведущего ожесточенную борьбу, порой бесконечную, с могучими силами Тьмы, Зла[2].

Несмотря на большое количество разнообразных писателей, основоположником жанра фэнтези, в современном понимании, до сих пор традиционно считается Джон Рональд Руэл Толкин (1892-1973) - английский писатель, литературовед. Мировую известность ему принесла эпопея о "Средиземье": "Хоббит, или Туда и обратно" (1937), "Властелин колец" (1954-1955) и "Сильмариллион" (изданный сыном Толкина в 1977). Сам Толкин определял жанр своих произведений о Средиземье как "фэери" (от англ. fairy - сказочный, волшебный). Однако принципиальное отличие этого жанра от сказок заключается в том, что все чудеса имеют закономерный и вполне объяснимый характер.

Фэнтези-произведения - это всегда остросюжетная история, которая увлекает читателя в новый, волшебный мир. Сегодня фэнтези стало общепринятой частью поп-культуры, отношение к жанру более уважительное. Даже взрослые люди, далёкие от «гиковской» субкультуры, читают фэнтези-романы, рассматривая их как литературу для отдыха и размышлений.

Объединение фэнтезийных сюжетов с элементами других жанров. Например, существует городское фэнтези, где герой-детектив расследует магические преступления, или фэнтези-детективы, сочетающие логику расследования с волшебными реалиями. Также набирает популярность «боевое фэнтези» - книги, где упор сделан на непрерывный экшен, сражения, погони.

Развитие поджанров, например, романтического фэнтези, где на первый план выходят любовные линии и отношения между героями. Отдельно выделяют популярный сегмент «академка» - истории про магические академии, колледжи или университеты, где учатся молодые маги.

Влияние на другие сферы, в частности на видеоигры. Существует большое количество экшен-игр в жанре фэнтези, фэнтези-стратегии и фэнтези-приключенческие игры. Дальше на рассмотрение мы берем «Гарри Поттера». История о молодом волшебнике, который сражается с силами зла, покорила миллионы сердец читателей. Цикл романов из семи книг пользуется популярностью не только у детей и подростков, но и у взрослой аудитории. Свою историю «Гарри Поттер» начинает в июне 1997 года, когда была опубликована первая книга Джоан Кэтлин Роулинг - «Гарри Поттер и философский камень». Произведение достаточно быстро становится популярным, тиражи растут в геометрической прогрессии. Начиная с четвертой части - «Кубка Огня», все последующие книги бьют мировые рекорды по продажам. Книги становятся бестселлерами и являются ими по сей день. Сегодня мы имеем целое поколение, которое выросло вместе с Гарри Поттером. На наших глазах Поттер превратился в отдельный культурный феномен. Книги переведены на 67 языков и количество проданных экземпляров перевалило за полмиллиарда[3].

Эта история о мальчике - Гарри, который в очень раннем возрасте лишился своих родителей, по вине главного антагониста истории - Лорда Волан - де- Морта. Потеряв колоссально много своих сил на убийство молодой семьи, темный лорд вынужден много лет скрываться от мира, в надежде, что однажды вся былая мощь вернется к нему. В первых трех книгах Гарри удачно мешает самому опасному волшебнику всех времен обрести тело и силу, но в четвертой книге Волан-де-Морт возвращает себе все свое могущество. Цель жизни главного героя - это спасти мир от хаоса и страданий, которые несет с собой злодей. При помощи и поддержке своих друзей, наставников и всех небезразличных волшебников, неся при этом колоссальные потери, Гарри Поттер выигрывает эту войну. естественно -это опять же очень интересный сюжет. Целый новый мир, новый лексикон, который на сегодняшний день уже привычен очень многим людям, огромное количество сказочных, магических животных, и сила, которая отличает магов от магов (обычных людей). Чтение «Гарри Поттера» - это очень приятный, не напрягающий, но при этом интересный побег от реальности, который привлекателен для многих возрастных групп.

Дети, читая Поттера, восхищаются именно силой героев - как физическим превосходством (сила от обладания волшебными предметами, существами), так и силой их духа, решительностью, которой порой не хватает им в реальной жизни. Для более взрослых людей - это способ ненадолго уйти от ежедневных проблем, забот и ответственности, ненадолго забыться и вернуться в детство. В этой истории достаточно четко понятно, где добро, а где зло. Редко, когда герои кардинально меняются, переходя из одной категории в другую. Но при этом до последней книги так же присутствует интрига, подогревается интерес читателей неожиданными поворотами в истории. (как пример можно взять факт того, что Гарри Поттер являлся одним из семи крестражей - частичкой души Волан-де-Морта).

И последним разберем серию романов американской писательницы Стефани Майер - «Сумерки». Первая из четырех книг- «Сумерки» была выпущена осенью 2005 года. Книга моментально стала бестселлером[4]. На волне успеха, в последующие несколько лет Майер выпустила еще три книги, которые не уступали популярности друг другу.

История любви самой обычной девушки - подростка Беллы и вампира Эдварда в первую очередь была предназначена для подростковой аудитории. Но, как это часто бывает, читательская публика данных произведений вышла за пределы изначально поставленных рамок.

Истории о вампирах не новы: леденящий кровь Носферату, жуткий Дракула, если брать более современные истории, то вампиры из Блейда, которых ненавидишь с самого начала повествования. «Сумерки» - это совсем новый формат вампиров. Тут главный акцент делается уже не на их безграничной силе или же жуткой сущности, а на их безупречной внешности. Главный герой - это молодой парень, с идеальной внешностью, загадочным характером, который отличается от всех окружающих. И тот факт, что влюбляется он в самую заурядную девушку, является одной из главных причин популярности саги. Девочки - подростки, для которых писались эти книги, да и девушки, женщины постарше, часто проецируют данную ситуацию на себя: «А вот что если бы это была я...». Несложный язык, которым написаны книги, эпичность некоторых действий, романтичность героев, внешний лоск всего, что связано с этим миром - это все является рецептом огромного успеха данной «Саги»[5].

Моя гипотеза о том, что жанр фэнтези является популярной литературой для подростков и что чтение фэнтези формирует активную, творческую, гармонически развитую личность, подтвердилась полностью. Такой вывод я сделала на основе анкетирования, опроса пятиклассников, анализа статей на данную тему, беседы со школьным психологом.

С чтением всегда было связано духовное развитие человечества. Однако последние годы характеризуются резким падением интереса к печатному слову. Время досуга современный подросток всё чаще проводит перед телевизором или компьютером. И всё же, как я это выяснила, есть ещё подростки, которые с удовольствием читают художественную литературу.

Современные романтически настроенные подростки увлекаются жанром фэнтези. В ходе общения со сверстниками было выяснено, что чтение этих книг увлекает романтикой открытий неизведанного и необычайного, расширяет кругозор, развивает творческую фантазию и воображение. Основная черта фэнтези схватывается детьми очень чутко – естественность чуда, размытость границ между мирами, возможность невозможного.

В большинстве случаев опыт и знание жизни подросток черпает именно из книг. Вмешавшая в себя лучшие традиции классической литературы и фольклорную мудрость, фэнтези сегодня взяло на себя роль, которую ранее успешно выполняла реалистическая, классическая литература - воспитание личности.

Не стоит игнорировать предпочтения молодёжи. Часто бывает, что «поп-литература» становится единственным средством найти взаимопонимание между поколениями. Фэнтези – часть «поп - литературы», которая имеет эстетически достойные произведения, имеющие завидную и неугасающую популярность среди подростков.

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ АРХАИЗМОВ НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ТРИЛОГИИ «ПЁТР ПЕРВЫЙ» А.ТОЛСТОГО

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Аннотация: Наша статья посвящена исследованию функциональных возможностей архаизмов в трилогии А.Н. Толстого "Пётр Первый". В работе анализируется роль устаревших слов и выражений в создании исторического колорита, передаче атмосферы эпохи, раскрытии характеров персонажей и формировании авторской позиции. Архаизмы, как элементы языка, играют важную роль в формировании стилистической окраски текста, передают культурные и исторические реалии, а также способствуют созданию определенной атмосферности. В работе применяются методы лексикографии, контекстного анализа и стилистического анализа, что позволяет выделить основные функции архаизмов в различных произведениях литературы.

Ключевые слова: архаизмы, функциональные возможности, «Пётр Первый», пассивная лексика, исторический колорит, исторический роман.

Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of the functional potential of archaisms in A. N. Tolstoy's trilogy "Peter the First." The research analyzes the role of obsolete words and expressions in creating historical color, conveying the atmosphere of the era, revealing the characters' personalities, and shaping the author's perspective. Archaisms, as elements of language, play an essential role in forming the stylistic tone of the text, reflecting cultural and historical realities, and contributing to the overall atmospheric depth. The study employs methods of lexicography, contextual analysis, and stylistic analysis, which make it possible to identify the main functions of archaisms in various literary works.

Keywords: archaisms, functional potential, *Peter the First*, passive vocabulary, historical color, historical novel.

Изучение архаизмов в художественном тексте представляет собой актуальную задачу современной лингвистики и литературоведения. Архаизмы, как элементы устаревшей лексики, являются очень важным средством создания исторического колорита, выражения атмосферы эпохи и освещения авторского замысла. Трилогия А.Н. Толстого "Пётр Первый" является ярким примером исторического романа, в котором архаизмы играют важную роль в формировании художественного мира произведения. Исследование функциональных возможностей архаизмов в данном контексте позволяет глубже понять особенности языка и стиля писателя, а также раскрыть механизмы создания исторической достоверности в художественной литературе. В условиях когда растёт интерес к исторической прозе и необходимости сохранения культурного наследия, особое значение приобретает изучение архаизмов в произведениях классической литературы.

Вопросы использования архаизмов в художественной литературе рассматривались в работах многих лингвистов и литературоведов. Исследовались общие закономерности функционирования устаревшей лексики, ее роль в создании исторического колорита и характеристике персонажей (Виноградов В.В., Шанский Н.М., Костомаров В.Г.). Отдельные аспекты использования архаизмов в произведениях А.Н. Толстого, в том числе в трилогии "Пётр Первый", также затрагивались в литературоведческих работах, посвященных анализу языка и стиля писателя (Крюкова Л.А., Петров С.М.). Однако, комплексное исследование функциональных возможностей архаизмов в трилогии "Пётр Первый" с применением современных лингвистических методов, представляется недостаточно разработанным.

Теоретическая значимость работы заключается в расширении и углублении знаний о функциональных возможностях архаизмов в художественном тексте. Результаты исследования могут быть использованы в дальнейших лингвистических и литературоведческих исследованиях, посвященных изучению языка и стиля писателей, а также анализу исторической прозы.

В процессе своего исторического развития словарь русского языка, как отмечается в научной литературе, постоянно изменяется и совершенствуется. Его развитие определяется процессом непрерывного пополнения лексики за счёт новых слов. Одновременно с этим происходит и обратный процесс – исчезновение из её состава архаизмов. По мнению Н.М. Шанского, этот процесс не является определяющим, но сильно сказывается на облике словарного состава языка. [9. С. 28]

В лингвистической литературе зависимости от причин устарелости устаревшая лексика подразделяется на две группы: 1) историзмы – слова, семантика которых указывает на классы исчезнувших предметов, видов деятельности, на устаревшие процессы труда, понятия духовной и материальной культуры, обычаи и т. д. То есть это слова, потерявшие свою денотативную основу; 2) архаизмы, лексемы, которые в отличие от историзмов как языковые знаки утратили только одну свою сторону, обозначающее (так как они вытеснены другими словами) обозначаемое их получило другое наименование. [4. С. 34-40]

Архаизмы играют важную роль в передаче атмосферных деталей петровской эпохи. Использование устаревших слов и выражений создает ощущение времени, а также помогает читателю лучше понять быт, обычаи и нравы людей XVII-XVIII веков. Включение в текст лексики, такой как "бояре", "терем", "выворотень" и "витязь", способствует более полному и достоверному изображению жизни и общественного устройства того времени.

Язык, используемый в произведении, словно машина времени, переносит читателя в эпоху Петра Первого. Архаизмы, словно мостики, соединяют наше современное понимание с исторической реальностью того времени. Они не просто украшают текст, а воссоздают уникальный лексический колорит эпохи, делая повествование не только стилистически выразительным, но и исторически убедительным.

Примеры архаизмов, такие как "государев веленья" и "житие святых", служат для создания особой атмосферы. Они передают религиозность и духовность эпохи, а также подчеркивают авторитет и связь правителя с народом. Благодаря этим языковым элементам, читатель не просто узнает об истории, но и ощущает её.

Архаизмы в речи персонажей служат не только для создания колорита, но и для демонстрации их социального положения и уровня образования. Различия в использовании устаревших и современных языковых средств позволяют автору подчеркнуть пропасть между, скажем, высокопоставленными вельможами и учеными, чья речь насыщена архаичными конструкциями, и простыми людьми, чьи высказывания ближе к современному языку, что отражает их разный доступ к знаниям.

Автор "Петра Первого" мастерски использует архаизмы для создания индивидуальных речевых портретов своих героев. Устаревшие слова становятся маркером уникальности каждого персонажа. Например, речевой стиль Меншикова, пропитанный старинными выражениями, подчеркивает его укорененность в традициях. В то же время, речь молодых героев, включающая современные элементы, говорит об их устремленности к переменам.

Детальное изучение речи персонажей раскрывает их сущность. Так, речь Екатерины, богатая архаизмами и эмоционально насыщенными эпитетами, указывает на ее образованность и социальное положение. Персонажи из низших слоев общества, напротив, используют более простую лексику, что отражает их место в социальной структуре.

В произведениях А.Н. Толстого архаизмы играют значительную роль, выходя за рамки простого создания исторического фона и портретов персонажей. Они становятся средством выражения авторской позиции, позволяя писателю выделить свою точку зрения на события и явления прошлого. Благодаря этому читатель получает возможность лучше понять критическое отношение Толстого к определенным историческим процессам. Кроме того, использование архаизмов способствует стилистическому единству произведения, обогащает текст, создает ощущение подлинности и помогает сформировать многогранный, глубокий образ эпохи.

Таким образом, архаизмы в трилогии "Пётр Первый" А.Н. Толстого выполняют важную функциональную нагрузку, помогая не только создать исторический колорит, но и раскрыть характеры персонажей, их социальный статус и эмоциональный фон произведения. Исследование этой темы может глубже повысить понимание как произведения, так и его исторического фона.

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“МУНОЖОТ” АСАРИНИНГ ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРГА ТАРЖИМАЛАРИ ТАЖРИБАСИДАН

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Аннотация: *Мазкур маъруза теисларида асосан Алишер Навоийнинг асарлари ва унинг “Муножот” асарининг хорижий тилларга таржималари ҳақидаги танқидий фикр*мулоҳазалар ҳамда Муножот асарининг чет тилларга таржималари ҳақидаги лойиҳа мухтасар баён қилинган.*

Калит сўзлар: *Муножот, Хамса, бу асарларга танқидий фикрлар, таржима, табдил*

Алишер Навоийнинг “Муножот”и – жаҳон адабиётининг буюк асарларидан деб эътироф этилишга лойиқ асар. У мусулмон Шарқ адабиётида анъанавий ўзига хос жанр ҳисобланади. Буюк адибларнинг Аллоҳга яқин бўлганликлари сабаби ҳаёти поёнини сезган маҳалда ўз ҳаёти ва ижоди ҳақида Аллоҳ олдида ҳисобот бериб, шу пайтгача ҳеч кимга изҳори дил қилмаган, ўзидан ўзгага сир бўлган ҳолати, дил изҳори ва иқрори, тавба-тазаррусини ёзиб қолдириши мумтоз адабий жараёнга хос ноёб ва гениал ҳодиса ҳисобланади.. Бундай ҳолатни италянлардан Алигйери Данте, олмонлардан Йоханн Волфганг Гёте, руслардан Лев Толстой ўз бошидан кечирганлар. Аммо улардан аввал Аврелий Августин, форс шоири Абдуллоҳ Ансорий, туркийзабон Юнус Эмро, Аҳмад

Яссавий ва Алишер Навоий ўз муножотлари матнини мустақил асар сифатида ўз куллиётларига сўзбоши ёки илова тарзида мустақил асар сифатида ёзиб қолдиришган.

Амир Алишер Навоий ҳаёти ва ижоди рус олимлари Е.Э.Бертелс, Н.И.Конрад, олмон олимларидан М. Хартманн, Ҳ. Вамбери, З. Клайнмихел, В.Перч, А. Курелла, Б. Келлнер-Ҳайнкеле), Францияда Э.Блоше, Б. де Вербело, Франсуа де Бернье ва бошқалар томонидан теран таҳлил этилган. Ўзбекистонда эса бутун бир Навоийшунос олимлар авлоди – Ҳамид Сулаймон, Абдуқодир Ҳайитметов, Азиз Қаюмов, Воҳид Зоҳидов, Суйима Ғаниева, Иброҳим Ҳаққул, .Исҳоқов, Абдулла Аъзам, Шухрат Сироҷиддинов, Олимжон Давлатов, Султонмурод Олим, Нусратилла Жумаҳўжа, Сувон Мели, Зухриддин Исомиддинов ва бошқа тадқиқотчилар шаклланиб улгурди.

Бу саъй-ҳаракатлар ва изланшларнинг умумий томонлари билан бирга, айрим фарқли хулоса ва натижалари ҳам кўзга ташланади. Ҳазрат Навоий Афғонистонда туғилиб ўсган ва асосий умри-ю ижоди ўша маконда ўтган бўлса-да, ўзбек шеърини султонининг кенг қамровли ҳаёти ва серқирра ижоди ҳақидаги тадқиқотлар асосан Ўзбекистонда амалга оширилиб келинмоқда.

Бироқ ҳазратнинг фуқаролиги ва миллий мансублиги масаласида чет эл, хусусан Олмонияда афғон, туб миллати ўзбек эмас, балки уйғур дегувчилар бор (Ингеборг Балдауф). Алишер Навоийнинг бош асари „Ҳамса“ хусусида ҳам айрим гайри-илмий фикр-мулоҳазалар йўқ эмас. Чунончи Навоий қаламига мансуб „Ҳамса“ дostonлар мажмуасини гоҳ Низомий „Ҳамса“сидан таржима, гоҳида эса бошқа „Ҳамса“лар (Низомий, Дехлавий, Жомий) га таклид деган жиддий илмий таҳлилларга асосланмаган чалкаш ва нотўғри хулосалар ҳам борки, бу ҳолат илмий жамоатчиликни ҳайрон қолдириб, ёш олимларни тўғри йўлдан оздириши мумкин.

Худди шундай турли фикрлилик ҳазратнинг умри поёнида битилган „Муножот“ асари ҳақида ҳам учрайди. Айримлар бу асарни Алишер Навоий тириклигида ўзи раҳбарлигида яратилган „Куллиётга“ Кириш сўз деб қарашса (О. Лаванд, Ҳ. Сулаймон), бошқалар бу фикрга қўшилмай (С. Ғаниева, А. Аъзам), „Муножот“ни ноёб мустақил асар сифатида баҳолашмоқда.

Ўзбекистонда Алишер Навоий ижоди қанчалар қамровли ўрганилиб, ҳазратнинг турли танланган асарлари ва антологиялари яратилмасин, уларда XX аср ўрталаригача Навоий ижодига мансуб Муножот асари ҳақида ҳеч гап айтилмаган эди. Ўтган асрнинг 60-70 йилларида аввал Ҳамид Сулаймон, кейинроқ Суйима Ғаниева каби адабиётчиларнинг чет эл сафарлари бошланиб, шунда Ҳазрат Навоийнинг қаламига мансуб мутлоқ янги асар – „Муножот“ илк бор кашф қилинган. У Ўзбекистонда биринчи марта «Ёшлик» журналида (1990, 6-сон. Нашрга тайёрловчи С. Ғаниева), кейин эса, «Боқий сатрлар» сериясида 1991 йилда алоҳида араб ва кирилл ёзувида (С. Ғаниева), рус тилида С. Ғаниева таржимасида Москвада нашр этиладиган «Литературная газета»да, шунингдек инглиз, олмон, француз, испан, араб, ҳинд, форс, урду, дари тилларида ҳам чоп этилган («Ўзбекистон» журнали, 1990, 11-12-сонларига қаранг). Мазкур асарни Суйима Ғаниева 1991 йилда эълон қилган ва „Шарқ“ нашриётида сувенир китоб шаклида чоп эттирган. Унда асарнинг араб ёзувидаги эски ўзбекча матни ва шу матннинг Суйима Ғаниева ижросидаги ҳозирги ўзбек тилга амалга оширилган табдили, аслиятнинг Суйима Ғаниева томонидан русча таржимаси ва шу рус тилидаги вариантдан ўгирилган олмонча (Дора Баклитская), инглизча (Н. Гоголицина) ва форсийга ағдарилган таржималари жой олган.

Орадан бироз вақт ўтгач 1991 йилда Ғ. Фулом нашриётида шу асарнинг Суйима опа нашрга тайёрлаган варианты ҳам чоп этилдики, бу икки нашр адабиётшуносларнинг эътиборини ўзига қаратиб, мазкур аср танқиди ва таҳлиliga

бағишланган илмий ва илмий-оммабоп тадқиқотлар амалга оширила бошлади. Айниқса асли математика олими бўлган академик Абдулла Аъзамнинг асар шарҳи ва табдилидан иборат рисоласи, Сувон Мелининг каттагина қиёсий-таҳлилий мақоласи, шу асарнинг ёзувчи Музаффар Мирзо, Зухриддин Исомиддинов ва бошқалар бажарган янгича ўзбекча табдиллари жамоатчилик эътиборига туша бошлади.

С. Ғаниева “Муножот”нинг ёзилиши сабаблари ҳақида ҳам сўз юритиб шундай дейди: “Маълумки, Навоий ҳаётининг охирида бирмунча йиллар аввал юраги тубидан ўрин олган ҳаж сафари иштиёқи яна оловланади. У 1499-1500-йиллар давомида бир неча марта бевосита ва билвосита – яқинлари орқали Ҳусайн Бойқародан ҳаж сафарига изн сўрайди. Ҳар гал султон аввалига ижозат берар, лекин дарҳол ўзи шахсан шоир хузурига ташриф буюриб, сафарни қолдиришга кўндириб қайтар ёхуд энг нозик дўстларни орага қўйиб шоирни ахдидан қайтаришга муваффақ бўлар эди. Навоийнинг “Вақфия”да ёзишча, “икки орзу риштасидан (бири ҳаж, иккинчиси – ижод – С.Г‘.) ўзгаким, гириҳи кўнглум пардасидин ечилмади ва икки мурод ғунчасидин ўзгаким, тугуни жоним гулшанидин очилмади:

Мениким бу савдо низор айлади,

Ҳавас илгида бекарор айлади.

Не имонки, топқай қарор-у сукун,

Бировким, бу фикр этгай они забун”.

Бу орзуси рўёбга чиқмаслигига кўзи етган чоғларида Навоий руҳий азоблар гирдобиди қолар, ҳар қандай расмий, норасмий давлат юмушлари-ю мадад истаб келувчилардан ғоят толиқар эди, албатта. “Муножот”даги “Илоҳи, эмди ҳамким, барчадин кечмак хаёлин қилурмен, ўзлугум билан кеча олмон яқин билурмен. Илоҳи, андоққи, бу балоларга солдинг, қутқор ва андоқким, бу ибтилоларга киюрдунг, чиқор”, дея илтижо қилиши шоирнинг юқорида ёдга олинган тушкун кайфиятидан дарак беради. Шу билан бирга ҳаммадан воз кечиш мумкин ва осон, лекин “ўзлуги”дан кечиш мутлақо мумкин эмас, бу аниқ. Бинобарин, “ўзлук”ни муқаддас сақламоққа, уни таҳлика ва лоқайдликлардан халос этмоққа интилиш ниҳоятда зарур, деган шоирнинг юксак эътиқодини юзага чиқаради”.

Ҳазрат Навоийнинг “Муножот” асари ҳақида тўлиқроқ тасаввур олиш учун махсус мақола ёзган адабиётшунос олим Сувон Мелининг “Муножот поэтикасида қиёс” номли мақоласи билан ҳурматли китобхонлар танишиб чиқишларини истар эдик. Олим ўз мақоласида “Муножот” асари ҳақида нисбатан батафсил қиёсий филологик таҳлил тақдим этади (Қаранг: С.Мели: “Сўзу сўз”.Тошкент, ШАРҚ. 2020.).

Камина ушбу буюк асарни олмон тилига ўгиришга киришиб, шунга такрор амин бўлдимки, мумтоз адабиётимиз, айниқса Алишер Навоийдек бетакрор сўз устаси ва мутафаккир зотининг тили ва услубини тушуниш ва қайта яратиш ғоят мураккаб ва машаққатли жараён. Бундай асарларни идрок этиш учун тасаввуф таълимоти ва амалиётини жиддий ўрганиш кераклиги аён бўладики, камина бу машаққатли босқични Алишер Навоий ғазалиётидан таржималар қилганимдаёқ чуқур ҳис қилганман ва ҳазрат таваллудининг 580 йиллигига бағишлаб унинг 300 ғазалини олмон тилида ғазал шаклда “қайта яратишга” журъат қилдим (бу таржималаримнинг 100 таси 2021 йил “Адабиёт” нашриёти чоп этди ҳам). Бу китобим ўша йилнинг ўзидаёқ Олмониядаги Ўзбекистон элчихонаси ташаббуси билан Берлин ва Фрайбург шаҳарларида икки бор қайта нашр этирилиб, олмонзабон ўқувчиларга тарқатила бошланди. Шундан сўнг ушмамиз мега навбатдаги таржимангиз Навоийнинг Хамсаси бўлсин, дейишди. Бундай мушкул ишни бажаришни ўйласам, бу корга каминанинг на ақли, ва на умри етмаслигига амин бўлиб юрганимда, олмониялик туркшунос олимлар менга

“Навойнинг энг буюк асари “Муножот” ҳисобланади, Сиз шуни таржима қилинг”, деб тавсия этишганди.

Бундай бетакрор асарни Алишер Навойнинг 2026 йилда нишонландиган 585 йиллиги муносабати билан Ўзбекистон давлат жаҳон тиллари университети ва Тошкент давлат Шарқшунослик университетида ўқитилаётган 20 га яқин чет тилларга ҳам таржимасини қилиш таклифи билан ректоримиз Илҳомжон Тухтасиновга мурожаат қилдим. Инноватив таклифларни ҳамisha очик чеҳра билан қабул қиладиган, ўзи таржимашунос раҳбаримиз бу ғояни маъқуллаб, университетидаги тегишли мутахассисларга топшириқ бердилар. Таржимага рағбати бор ҳамкасбларга биз Алишер Навойнинг “Муножот” асарини адабиётшунос олима Суйима Ғаниева тайёрлаган табдилини аслият сифатида тарқатдик ва маълум фурсатдан сўнг улардан таржималарни қабул қилиб олдик. Қизиғи шуки, айрим чет тилларга аслиятнинг бир неча таржима вариантлари, жумладан: инглиз, олмон ва рус тилларига 3 тадан, француз, испан ва шарқ тилларига 2 тадан таржималар тақдим этилди. Бу алтернатив таржималарнинг энг адекват вариантини танлаб олиш учун шу тиллардан тилшунос ва таржимашунослардан экспертлар комиссияларини ташкил қилдик. Натижада нисбатан аслиймонанд таржималар аниқланди ва бўлажак таржималар мажмуаси вужудга келди. Мазкур амалиёт дастлабки уриниш бўлгани сабабли уларда бир тарафдан лисоний (семантик ва услубий) хато ва нуқсонлар, бошқа тарафдан тасаввуфий термин ва тушунчалар талқинида англашилмовчилик бўлиши табиий ҳолатки, жаҳон таржимачилигида фақат Гётенинг шоҳасари Фаустни инглиз тилга 51, фаранг тилига 27, рус тига 11, ўзбек тилига 2 та таржимавий уринишлар содир бўлганки, Навойнинг тасаввуфона асарлари такрорий таржималари пайдо бўлишини ҳам табиий ҳол деб билсак бўлади. Мақсадимиз – Алишер Навой феноменини жаҳоннинг асосий тилларида имкон қадар адекват ва муқобил тарзда қайта яратиш ҳамда ул ҳазратга тобора яқинлашиш орқали миллий адабиётимиз султонини жаҳон адабиёти саҳнасида бор бўй-басти, салоҳияти билан кўрсатиш - 21 аср таржимачилигимизнинг асосий долзарб вазфаларидан деб биламиз.

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LOST IN ABUNDANCE: NAVIGATING THE PARADOX OF CHOICE IN 21ST - CENTURY FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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“Too many choices can lead to no choice at all.” -Barry Schwartz

Abstract. In the 21st century, the field of foreign language education has witnessed an unprecedented expansion of learning opportunities. From mobile applications to online universities, learners now face a seemingly infinite array of digital tools. However, this abundance often leads to confusion and decreased motivation - a phenomenon known as the ‘paradox of choice’. This article examines the causes and effects of this issue, drawing on psychological, technological, and pedagogical perspectives.

Keywords: choice overload, digital learning, foreign language teaching, learner motivation, online education, decision-making, pedagogy.

Аннотация. В XXI веке сфера обучения иностранным языкам стала свидетелем беспрецедентного расширения возможностей обучения. От мобильных приложений до онлайн-университетов учащиеся сталкиваются с, казалось бы, бесконечным множеством цифровых инструментов. Однако это изобилие часто приводит к путанице и снижению мотивации - феномену, известному как «парадокс выбора». В данной статье рассматриваются причины и последствия этой проблемы с точки зрения психологии, технологий и педагогики.

Ключевые слова: перегрузка выбором, цифровое обучение, преподавание иностранных языков, мотивация учащихся, онлайн-образование, принятие решений, педагогика.

Абстракт. 21-asrda chet tillarini o'qitish sohasi o'rganish imkoniyatlarining misli ko'rilmagan kengayishiga guvoh bo'ldi. Mobil ilovalardan tortib onlayn universitetlargacha o'quvchilar endi cheksiz ko'rinadigan raqamli vositalarga duch kelishadi. Biroq, bu mo'l-ko'llik ko'pincha chalkashliklarga va motivatsiyaning pasayishiga olib keladi - bu "tanlov paradoksi" deb nomlanuvchi hodisa. Ushbu maqola psixologik, texnologik va pedagogik nuqtai nazardan kelib chiqib, ushbu muammoning sabablari va oqibatlarini o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tanlovning haddan tashqari yuklanishi, raqamli o'rganish, chet tilini o'rgatish, o'quvchilar motivatsiyasi, onlayn ta'lim, qaror qabul qilish, pedagogika.

The modern learner is surrounded by information and technology. Language learning in particular has become easier to access but harder to navigate. Learners can use Duolingo, BBC Learning English, Coursera, or countless YouTube channels. Each promises fast progress and personalized instruction. Yet many learners report frustration when trying to choose between these tools. This situation reflects Barry Schwartz's (2004) theory of the paradox of choice - that more freedom can sometimes reduce satisfaction. In the context of foreign language learning, this paradox means that while technological abundance provides flexibility, it also creates uncertainty, distraction, and inconsistency in study habits. Many students begin learning with enthusiasm but lose motivation when they cannot decide which platform, method, or teacher suits them best. Therefore, the problem is not a lack of opportunities, but rather the inability to manage and select from the overwhelming variety of them. Understanding how to guide learners in this environment is crucial for effective 21st-century pedagogy.

Existing Problems within the Topic

The availability of thousands of online resources has created several pedagogical and psychological problems. Firstly, learners suffer from "decision fatigue." Constantly comparing websites, apps, and teachers consumes mental energy and discourages long-term learning (Iyengar & Lepper, 2000). Secondly, unfiltered online materials often lack quality assurance. For example, on YouTube, one can find both professional lessons and misleading amateur videos. Without proper digital literacy, learners may absorb incorrect information, grammatical errors, or culturally inappropriate examples. As a result, their language foundation becomes inconsistent and fragmented.

Another major issue is the lack of personalized guidance. Many students rely entirely on digital tools that cannot adapt to their emotional or motivational needs. They may jump from one resource to another, expecting faster results, but instead lose focus and confidence. Teachers, too, face difficulties in choosing among thousands of materials available online. This lack of structure often leads to irregular study habits and superficial learning, where students understand words but struggle to communicate effectively. In short, the

overabundance of digital resources, combined with insufficient teacher supervision and critical thinking skills, has created a serious challenge for both learners and educators in the 21st century.

In Uzbekistan, the problem is visible in universities where students are encouraged to use online resources but rarely guided on how to select them. Many switch between Duolingo, Memrise, Telegram learning channels, and online dictionaries without following a structured curriculum. Teachers, too, sometimes struggle to integrate modern resources into traditional classrooms. According to UNESCO (2021), over 60% of students in Central Asia face difficulties identifying credible educational content online.

To overcome the paradox of choice in language learning, both learners and educators must adopt guided selection and digital discipline. Teachers can serve as “curators” rather than mere transmitters of knowledge. For instance, when teaching vocabulary, instructors might recommend only three trusted tools: Duolingo for gamified practice, Quizlet for flashcards, and BBC Learning English for contextual listening. This reduces confusion and supports habit formation.

Educational institutions can also implement digital literacy courses where students learn to evaluate online materials based on credibility, interactivity, and cultural relevance. For example, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies introduced workshops on “Effective Online Language Learning” in 2023, helping students evaluate global platforms like Coursera and EdX. Such institutional frameworks build confidence and autonomy in learners while preserving structure. Moreover, blended learning models—where traditional classroom instruction is combined with carefully selected online resources—can create a more balanced and sustainable educational environment.

In a blended system, students might attend regular grammar or speaking lessons at university while practicing vocabulary or listening skills through online platforms at home. This integration allows learners to experience both human interaction and digital flexibility. Teachers can monitor students’ progress online and provide individual feedback during face-to-face sessions. Such collaboration between technology and pedagogy ensures that learners use digital tools purposefully rather than randomly. Ultimately, the solution to the paradox of choice is not to limit technological options, but to teach learners how to navigate them effectively and meaningfully.

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ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA O'QITISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLARI

CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES AND REMEDIAL STRATEGIES IN TODAY'S EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article explores the key challenges faced in the modern educational process and presents effective strategies to overcome them. It examines issues such as unequal access to quality education, the overreliance on traditional teaching methods, the lack of motivation among students, insufficient use of technology, and the need for teachers' continuous professional development. Furthermore, the paper discusses the impact of digital transformation, globalization, and changing learning environments on both teachers and learners. Various innovative approaches, including the integration of digital tools, interactive teaching methods, individualized learning, and collaboration between educators and policymakers, are proposed as solutions.

Key words: modern education, educational problems, digital learning, innovative teaching, student motivation, teacher development, learning accessibility, educational reform.

Education in the modern world stands at a crossroads where progress and crisis coexist. The twenty-first century has transformed nearly every aspect of human life, and education has been forced to evolve within this rapid pace of change. While technological innovation, global connectivity, and pedagogical research have expanded opportunities for learning, the system also faces persistent and emerging problems that challenge its effectiveness, equity, and purpose. Understanding these issues in depth is vital, as the quality of education directly influences social stability, economic development, and individual growth. The modern educational process is shaped by complex interactions between societal expectations, government policy, technological change, and the human dimension of teaching and learning. Within this dynamic landscape, educators and policymakers must strive to balance innovation with inclusion, ensuring that the system not only transmits knowledge but also nurtures the whole person.

One of the most serious problems in the modern educational process is the growing inequality in access to quality learning opportunities. Despite the global rhetoric of inclusive education, a large proportion of learners continue to face barriers linked to geography, socioeconomic status, language, and disability. Students in rural or under-resourced areas often study in schools that lack qualified teachers, technological tools, and adequate materials. In contrast, urban and private institutions enjoy advanced infrastructure and access to digital resources. This imbalance deepens social divides and contradicts the foundational principle of education as a universal right. Moreover, the digital revolution, while offering new avenues for learning, has simultaneously widened the gap between those who can afford technology and those who cannot. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed this disparity dramatically, as millions of students were unable to participate in remote learning due to lack of devices or internet connectivity.

Thus, equality of access remains a moral and practical challenge that requires not only funding but a rethinking of how educational systems distribute resources and support.

Technology itself represents both a problem and a potential solution. When integrated thoughtfully, digital tools can personalize instruction, make learning interactive, and connect classrooms across continents. However, the rapid introduction of technology without proper pedagogical grounding often leads to superficial results. Many teachers feel unprepared to use digital tools effectively, while others rely on them excessively, allowing technology to substitute rather than support good teaching. The abundance of online information also creates challenges in distinguishing credible sources from misinformation, which makes digital literacy a new and urgent skill. Additionally, screen dependence has contributed to declining attention spans and reduced face-to-face communication skills among students. To harness technology productively, educational institutions must invest not only in infrastructure but also in teacher training and ethical frameworks that ensure technology enhances rather than replaces human interaction. The professional status and working conditions of teachers represent another critical dimension of the problem. Teachers are the heart of education, yet in many countries they are undervalued, underpaid, and overburdened with administrative tasks that leave little time for innovation or self-development. The profession's declining prestige discourages talented young people from entering teaching, leading to shortages and burnout among existing staff. Professional development opportunities are often limited or poorly aligned with teachers' real needs. In the modern educational process, teachers must constantly update their skills to keep pace with changes in pedagogy, curriculum, and technology. Therefore, continuous, high-quality professional training and supportive school cultures are indispensable. Recognizing teaching as a form of creative, intellectual, and social work rather than routine delivery of information is the first step toward improving educational quality at every level.[1]

Cultural relevance and inclusivity are other aspects that deserve careful reflection. Modern societies are increasingly diverse, with classrooms representing multiple languages, identities, and worldviews. Yet many educational systems still follow a monocultural curriculum that privileges dominant perspectives while marginalizing others. This lack of inclusivity not only alienates minority students but also deprives all learners of the opportunity to engage with diverse ideas. Education should cultivate empathy, respect, and intercultural competence, preparing students to live in pluralistic societies. Inclusive pedagogy requires teachers to recognize the unique experiences of each learner and adapt instruction accordingly. It also means challenging stereotypes and promoting equity through representation and voice. In the modern educational process, diversity is not an obstacle but a resource for richer learning. Assessment practices remain another deeply embedded problem. The global obsession with standardized testing has distorted educational priorities, reducing learning to what can be easily measured. Tests may reveal certain skills, but they cannot capture creativity, collaboration, or critical thinking. Excessive testing narrows curricula, discourages innovation, and places unhealthy stress on both students and teachers. A more balanced approach would combine formative assessment - focused on feedback and improvement - with summative measures that evaluate broader competencies. Authentic assessment methods such as portfolios, project work, and presentations can provide a fuller picture of student growth. Shifting the purpose of assessment from ranking to learning would realign education with its true mission: the development of human potential.

Despite these formidable challenges, there are promising solutions emerging from educational research and practice. Many of these solutions are rooted in the principles of learner-centered education, which emphasizes active participation, collaboration, and the

development of critical consciousness. In this model, the teacher becomes a facilitator rather than a lecturer, guiding students as they construct their own understanding. Such approaches cultivate autonomy and lifelong learning skills, which are indispensable in a rapidly changing world. Integrating project-based learning, problem-solving tasks, and reflective dialogue can transform classrooms into spaces of inquiry rather than rote instruction. Moreover, linking academic learning with real-world contexts - through community projects, internships, and service learning-helps students see the relevance of their education. Another key solution lies in the professional empowerment of teachers. Providing opportunities for continuous learning, peer mentoring, and collaborative planning fosters innovation and confidence. Schools that create professional learning communities enable teachers to share best practices and collectively solve challenges. Governments and institutions must also ensure fair salaries, reasonable workloads, and recognition for teaching excellence. When teachers are trusted and respected as professionals, they are more likely to inspire and sustain high-quality learning experiences for students. [2]

Addressing students' emotional and psychological well-being requires systemic commitment. Schools should implement comprehensive programs for mental health support, peer mentoring, and counselling. Teachers, too, need training to recognize signs of stress or depression and to create compassionate classroom climates. Encouraging mindfulness, physical activity, and balanced workloads helps sustain motivation and resilience. Education cannot be separated from care; teaching and nurturing must coexist. The inclusion of diverse voices and experiences within education also represents an essential step toward justice and relevance. Teachers can incorporate multicultural perspectives into literature, history, and social studies, allowing students to see themselves and others reflected in what they learn. Language policies should support bilingualism and linguistic diversity, recognizing that multiple languages enrich rather than hinder learning. Inclusive education extends beyond disability accommodation; it embodies a philosophy that every student, regardless of background or ability, deserves meaningful participation and high expectations.

Finally, policy reform is needed to sustain these transformations. Governments must treat education not as an expense but as a long-term investment in human capital and democratic stability. Transparent, equitable funding systems are required to reduce disparities between regions and schools. Policymakers should collaborate closely with educators, researchers, and communities to design reforms grounded in evidence rather than ideology. Decentralized governance, where schools have greater autonomy to innovate, can encourage local creativity while maintaining accountability. [3] Evaluating policy success through holistic indicators such as student well-being, civic engagement, and lifelong learning - would provide a more authentic picture of educational progress than test scores alone.

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DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE CLASSROOM COMMUNICATION THROUGH ACTIVE LISTENING AND BODY LANGUAGE AWARENESS

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Abstract: This article explores the essential communication behaviors that influence the success of group discussions in educational contexts-active listening, respect, turn-taking (management of interruptions), and body language. Drawing upon theories from communication studies, educational psychology, and classroom interaction research, it emphasizes how active listening fosters comprehension and participation, respect builds trust and inclusion, regulated turn-taking maintains discussion flow, and body language reinforces or undermines verbal communication. By examining empirical and theoretical perspectives, the article demonstrates that these components are interdependent and collectively shape students’ engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking. The findings highlight that promoting respectful dialogue, minimizing disruptive interruptions, and increasing awareness of non-verbal cues can substantially enhance classroom discussions and cooperative learning outcomes.

Keywords: classroom communication, active listening, respect, turn-taking, body language, group discussion, collaborative learning.

In today’s learner-centered educational settings, effective communication is a key element of successful classroom interaction. Whether in small group discussions, project collaborations, or peer learning activities, communication enables students to share ideas, construct knowledge collectively, and develop critical thinking and social-emotional skills. Scholars such as Vygotsky (1978) and Mercer (2000) have emphasized that learning is a social process-language serves not only as a tool for conveying information but also for constructing shared understanding.

Within this context, four interconnected communication behaviors play a vital role in shaping the quality of group discussions: active listening, respect, turn-taking (or interruption management), and body language awareness. Active listening allows learners to fully engage with others’ ideas, ensuring mutual understanding and empathy (Rogers & Farson, 1987). Respect creates a safe psychological space where participants feel valued, which encourages participation and creativity (Anderson, Hildreth, & Howland, 2015). Turn-taking, or the management of interruptions, maintains order and fairness in discussions, preventing dominance and exclusion (Smith & Smith, 2016). Finally, body language-gestures, posture, facial expressions-communicates emotions and attitudes that can strengthen or weaken verbal messages (Mehrabian, 1971; Goman, 2011). This article examines how these elements function within classroom group discussions, drawing on existing research to highlight their educational implications. It aims to provide insights for educators and students seeking to cultivate communicative competence, collaborative dialogue, and mutual respect in learning environments.

Active listening extends beyond passive hearing-it involves focused attention, interpretation, and empathetic feedback (Rogers & Farson, 1987). In educational settings,

active listening plays a critical role in promoting comprehension and reflective thinking. When students listen attentively, they are able to paraphrase peers' ideas, ask clarifying questions, and connect new information to prior knowledge (Brown & Levinson, 1987). Studies show that classrooms emphasizing active listening foster greater student motivation and achievement (Gillies, 2019). Teachers who model active listening behaviors-such as nodding, summarizing, or responding with validating comments-help students internalize these skills. This reciprocal listening dynamic enhances both academic performance and interpersonal relationships (Mercer, 2000).

Respect functions as the moral and emotional foundation of effective communication. Anderson et al. (2015) argue that respect fosters psychological safety, allowing participants to share ideas without fear of embarrassment or rejection. In classrooms, respect translates into behaviors such as taking turns, acknowledging differing opinions, and providing constructive feedback rather than criticism. Research by Littlejohn and Foss (2010) suggests that mutual respect not only sustains group harmony but also nurtures inclusivity-essential in culturally and linguistically diverse classrooms. When students feel respected, they demonstrate higher levels of engagement, empathy, and responsibility in collaborative tasks. Interruptions are a common but complex feature of group communication. They can serve both constructive and disruptive functions. According to Smith and Smith (2016), well-timed interjections may clarify points or maintain topic focus, while frequent or dominating interruptions hinder equal participation. In educational discussions, poor interruption management often silences quieter students and fragments the group's cognitive flow. To promote fairness and inclusivity, educators can establish discussion norms such as hand-raising, speaking time limits, or round-robin formats (Johnson & Johnson, 2014). These structures teach learners conversational discipline and respect for others' contributions. Effective turn-taking promotes both efficiency and equity, key components of democratic classroom discourse (Mercer & Dawes, 2014).

Non-verbal communication accounts for much of the emotional and relational meaning in classroom interactions. Mehrabian (1971) found that gestures, posture, facial expressions, and tone convey up to 65% of a message's meaning. Positive body language-open posture, consistent eye contact, and nodding-signals attentiveness and support, encouraging speakers to continue. Conversely, negative cues-crossed arms, lack of eye contact, or fidgeting-may communicate disinterest or hostility, undermining verbal intent. In educational settings, teachers and students must be conscious of body language as both an expressive and interpretive skill. As Goman (2011) explains, congruence between verbal and non-verbal communication enhances authenticity and credibility. Training in non-verbal awareness can improve collaboration, emotional regulation, and classroom climate (Hargie, 2011).

The effectiveness of group discussions depends on how these four elements-active listening, respect, turn-taking, and body language-interact. Each reinforces the other: respect encourages active listening; active listening minimizes disruptive interruptions; structured turn-taking supports equitable participation; and positive body language enhances the emotional climate. Educational researchers such as Johnson and Johnson (2014) emphasize that cooperative learning environments thrive when communication behaviors align toward inclusivity and shared understanding. When educators explicitly teach and model these skills, students develop communicative competence that extends beyond the classroom, preparing them for academic, professional, and civic engagement.

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TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI - AN'ANAVIY TA'LIMDAN INNOVATSION TA'LIMGA YO'L

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ta'lim tizimining an'anaviy uslublari, ularning bosqichma-bosqich innovatsion ta'limga o'tish jarayonlari hamda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish bosqichlari tahlil qilingan. O'qitish va til o'rgatish jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalar, interaktiv metodlar va kreativ yondashuvlarning o'rni hamda ahamiyati ochib berilgan. Shuningdek, zamonaviy til ta'limining o'qish va o'qitishdagi roli, integrallashgan til ta'limi metodi orqali o'quvchilarda mustaqil fikrlash va ijodkorlik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim transformatsiyasi, kreativ yondashuv, an'anaviy ta'lim, innovatsion ta'lim, o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar ro'li, integrallashgan ta'lim tizimi, raqamli texnologiyalar, raqobatdosh kadrlar.

Annotation: This article analyzes the traditional methods of the education system, the gradual transition processes toward innovative education, and the developmental stages of the modern educational system. The study highlights the role and significance of digital technologies, interactive methods, and creative approaches in teaching and language learning. It also discusses the importance of modern language education in the teaching and learning process, focusing on the development of students' independent thinking and creativity through the integrated language education method.

Keywords: educational transformation, creative approach, traditional education, innovative education, roles of teachers and learners, integrated education system, digital technologies, competitive specialists.

Bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimi boshqa masalalardan farqli o'laroq eng muhim mavzular qatorida kelmoqda. Davlatimizni rivojlantirish, yurtimizni eng rivojlangan mamlakatlar

qatoriga qo'shish uchun bizga yetuk va har tomonlama malakali yosh kadrlar kerakli ekani bu barchamizga sir emas. "Shuningdek, bugungi kunda mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida kadrlar tayyorlash tizimining demokratik o'zgarishlar va bozor islohotlari talablariga muvofiq emasligi, o'quv jarayo-ning moddiy-texnika va axborot bazasi yetarli emasligi, yuqori malakali ilmiy-pedagog kadrlarning yetishmasligi, sifatli o'quv-uslubiy va ilmiy adabiyotlar hamda didaktik materiallarning kamligi, ta'lim tizimi, fan va ishlab chiqarish o'rtasida samarali o'zaro hamkorlik va o'zaro foydali integratsiyaning yo'qligi kadrlar tayyorlashning mavjud tizimidagi jiddiy kamchiliklar sirasiga kiradi." [2,26b.]. Aynan shunday kadrlarni yetishtirib berish va ularni yurtimiz kelajagi uchun masul shaxslar qatoriga qo'shishda ta'lim tizimi asosiy ro'l o'ynab kelmoqda. Ko'plab insonlarni nafaqat, har bir individni shaxs qatoriga qo'shish uchun va ularni yetuk, mustaqil fikrli shaxs darajasiga ko'tarish uchun ta'lim tizimining ahamiyati alohida o'rinda turadi. "Globallashuv sharoitida ta'lim shaxsni har tomonlama voyaga yetkazish, unda komillik va har tomonlama mutaxassisga xos sifatlarni shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi" [3,127b.].

Bunday ta'lim tizimi hozirgi raqamli texnologik jarayonlarda va zamonaviylashgan hayot tarzimiz uchun zerikarli va sodda hisoblanadi. Aynan o'quvchilar uchun bunday dars turlari yetarli darajada samara bera olmaydi. Isrtiqbolli kelajakka erishish uchun esa bizga va bizning "Yangi O'zbekiston"imizga yangicha fikrlaydigan kadrlar kerak. Bunday kadrlarni yetishtirish uchun yangi ruhdagi va yangicha tizimdagi ta'lim zarurati tug'iladi. Biz bunday zaruratni Innovatsion ta'lim bilan almashtirsak maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi deb o'ylaymiz. Shuning uchun ham ta'lim transformatsiyasi biz uchun ayni muaddaodir. Bizning maqsadimiz ham ta'limda muammolarni transformatsiya orqali hal etish va maqsadlarimizga erishish uchun ta'lim transformatsiyasi joriy etilishi jadallashtirish va ta'lim transformatsiyasi orqali erishiladigan yutuqlarini ko'rsatib berishdan iboratdir.

An'anaviy ta'lim tizimi uzoq yillar davomida o'qitishning asosiy shakli bo'lib, ta'lim jarayonida intizom, tartib va tizimlilikni ta'minlab kelgan. Uning asosiy afzalligi - o'qituvchining yetakchi rolida bo'lishi va o'quv jarayonining qat'iy nazorat ostida olib borilishi bo'lgan. Belgilangan dastur asosida izchil dars o'tish o'quvchilarda puxta bilim, mas'uliyat va intizomni shakllantirishga xizmat qilgan. Shuningdek, o'qituvchining tajribasi, nutq madaniyati va darsni tashkil etish ko'nikmalari ta'lim sifatini belgilovchi muhim omillar bo'lgan.

Bu tizim o'quvchilarda sabr, e'tibor va mehnatsevarlikni tarbiyalagan. Darslarning mantiqiy ketma-ketligi bilimlarning izchilligini ta'minlagan. Shu bois, an'anaviy o'qitish o'z davrida samarali tizim sifatida e'tirof etilgan. Biroq, uning ayrim kamchiliklari ham mavjud. Avvalo, o'quvchilarning faol ishtirokini va mustaqil fikrlash imkoniyatini cheklagan. O'qituvchi markazli yondashuv tufayli o'quvchilarda ijodkorlik va tanqidiy tafakkur yetarli darajada rivojlanmagan. Darslarning ko'p hollarda ma'ruza shaklida o'tilishi amaliy mashg'ulotlarni kamaytirgan. Shuningdek, sinflarda o'quvchilar sonining ko'pligi individual yondashuvni qiyinlashtirgan.

Bundan tashqari, an'anaviy tizimda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyati bo'lmagan yoki kamdan-kam, bu esa ta'limni zamon talablariga moslashtirishni sekinlashtirgan. Til o'rganishda ham bir qator kamchiliklar ko'zga tashlangan. Xususan til o'rganishda asosan grammatik qoidalar bilan cheklanib qolishgan. Suhbatlashishni o'rganish uchun darslardagi amaliyotning yo'qligi to'siq bo'lgan. Shunga qaramay, an'anaviy o'qitishdagi qat'iylik, izchillik va mehnatsevarlik kabi fazilatlar bugungi innovatsion ta'limda ham o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Shu sababli, hozirgi islohotlar an'anaviy tizimning foydali jihatlarni saqlab, uni interaktiv va raqamli metodlar bilan uyg'unlashtirib ta'lim transformatsiyasida qo'llash maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Ta'lim tizimini yanada isloh qilish o'ta dolzarb masala ekanini O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 29-apreldagi PF -5712 -son bilan "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi farmonidan bilib olsak bo'ladi [1]. Ushbu konsepsiya ta'lim tizimini tubdan yangilash, zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish, o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish, o'quv jarayonini xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirish va o'quvchilarda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishni maqsad qilgan. Konsepsiyada ham zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgani bejiz emas. Bugungi davrda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, internet, zamonaviy texnologiyalar yosh avlodning qon -qoniga singib ketganini va AI (Sun'iy Intellect) bir mo'jiza kabi hayotimizga kirib kelayotganini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, an'anviy uslubdagi ta'lim yoshlar uchun zerikarli deb o'ylayman. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonini yangilash va interaktiv metodlarni samarali joriy etishda hal qiluvchi o'rin tutadi. Raqamli texnologiyalar interaktiv ta'lim metodlarini kuchaytirib, ta'lim samaradorligi, o'quvchi faolligi va ijodkorligini oshiradi.

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MODERN TRENDS IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION AND THE ROLE OF DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article explores the major trends in modern language education through the lens of discourse theory. It argues that recent pedagogical innovations—from communicative and task-based learning to technology-enhanced and multilingual approaches—reflect a shift from teaching isolated grammatical structures to developing discourse competence. Language is viewed as social action: a means of constructing meaning, identity, and relationships within authentic communicative contexts. The paper examines how approaches such as CLIL, blended learning, and adaptive digital platforms integrate discourse principles by emphasizing interaction, context, and cultural awareness. It also highlights the growing importance of intercultural competence and translanguaging as essential dimensions of modern communicative practice. The study concludes that effective language education today is inherently discourse-oriented, aiming to prepare learners for meaningful participation in a multilingual and globalized world.

Keywords: discourse competence, language education, communicative approach, CLIL, technology-enhanced learning, multilingualism, intercultural communication.

In recent decades, language education has experienced a profound transformation influenced by globalization, technological advancement, and new theoretical developments in linguistics and discourse studies. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the ability to communicate across linguistic and cultural boundaries has become one of the most valuable competencies of the 21st century. Modern approaches to language education no longer view language merely as a system of grammar and vocabulary but as a form of

discourse—a socially and culturally situated mode of interaction through which people construct meaning, identity, and relationships [Gee, 2014, p. 21]. This discourse-oriented perspective has shaped nearly every modern trend in language teaching, from communicative and task-based methods to technology-enhanced learning and intercultural education.

Earlier methods such as Grammar-Translation or Audiolingualism treated language learning as the mechanical acquisition of structures. Learners memorized grammatical patterns and translated texts without necessarily understanding the communicative value of what they were saying. However, this approach failed to account for the fact that language operates as discourse-embedded in context, intention, and social interaction. The emergence of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in the 1970s marked a decisive shift from sentence-level grammar to discourse-level competence. As Richards and Rodgers [2014, p. 44] explain, CLT emphasizes the ability to use language appropriately in authentic contexts. Students are encouraged to participate in discussions, debates, interviews, and role-plays that replicate real communicative situations. Through these activities, they develop not only linguistic but also pragmatic and sociolinguistic skills, understanding how meaning changes depending on who speaks, to whom, and in what situation.

A related development, Task-Based Language Learning (TBLL), builds on discourse principles by engaging learners in meaningful tasks that require language use for real communicative purposes [Ellis, 2003, p. 35]. For instance, learners might collaborate to solve a problem, create a presentation, or write a report—activities that mirror authentic discourse practices. In such contexts, grammar and vocabulary emerge as tools for achieving communicative goals rather than as isolated objects of study. Language thus becomes a vehicle for participation in discourse, not a product to be memorized.

This discourse-centered orientation has also been reinforced by the integration of Technology-Enhanced Language Learning (TELL). Digital tools such as discussion forums, video calls, podcasts, and social media platforms immerse students in real-world discursive environments [Chapelle, 2010, p. 22]. Learners can now participate in online communities, exchange messages, or create digital content in the target language, interacting with authentic texts and speakers across the globe. Applications like Duolingo and ChatGPT provide interactive feedback, while digital storytelling and blogging platforms encourage learners to construct meaning through written and multimodal discourse [Godwin-Jones, 2018, p. 12]. The online world thus serves as both a classroom and a communicative arena where learners practice discourse skills in natural settings.

The development of blended and hybrid learning further strengthens the connection between discourse and pedagogy. Combining face-to-face and digital communication enables learners to experience language in multiple modes—spoken, written, and multimodal. In hybrid classrooms, discussions continue beyond physical meetings through online chats, collaborative documents, or learning management systems, allowing discourse to extend across time and space [Graham, 2013, p. 72]. Learners not only consume information but actively construct and share it, engaging in authentic communicative exchanges that mirror real-world discourse communities.

Another key innovation, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), also reflects a discourse-based view of language. When subjects such as science, history, or economics are taught through a foreign language, learners encounter academic and disciplinary discourse in that language [Coyle, Hood & Marsh, 2010, p. 41]. They acquire not only vocabulary and grammar but also ways of reasoning, arguing, and writing that are characteristic of the subject area. For example, writing a scientific report in English requires mastery of specific discourse conventions—objective tone, passive constructions, and logical

sequencing. CLIL thus situates language learning within the authentic discourses of academic life, encouraging cognitive and linguistic development simultaneously [Mehisto, 2012, p. 59].

Modern language education also recognizes that competence in discourse includes understanding cultural norms and values. This is the foundation of intercultural communicative competence, which enables learners to navigate different social and cultural contexts effectively [Byram, 1997, p. 34]. Intercultural competence involves not only knowing what to say but also how, when, and to whom to say it—skills that lie at the heart of discourse analysis. By integrating films, news articles, and cross-cultural projects into instruction, teachers help students interpret meaning beyond literal words and appreciate how discourse reflects cultural identity and power relations [Kramsch, 2013, p. 21]. In this way, language teaching becomes a process of socialization into diverse discursive worlds.

Recent technological innovations have introduced personalized and adaptive learning systems that analyze each learner's interactional patterns and provide tailored feedback. These systems simulate real-time discourse, offering learners opportunities to respond, negotiate meaning, and refine their communicative strategies [Heift & Schulze, 2015, p. 49]. Personalized instruction based on discourse data promotes active participation, as learners become aware of their pragmatic errors, cohesion strategies, and register choices. Such systems align with contemporary understandings of language as a dynamic, socially mediated practice rather than a fixed set of rules [Gilboy, Heinerichs & Pazzaglia, 2015, p. 88].

Another emerging perspective linked to discourse is the recognition of multilingualism and translanguaging. Traditional pedagogies often treated languages as separate, self-contained systems, but discourse-based research demonstrates that multilingual speakers fluidly draw on all their linguistic resources to make meaning [García & Wei, 2014, p. 42]. Translanguaging acknowledges that in real-life communication, speakers shift between languages and registers depending on context, audience, and purpose. Modern classrooms increasingly adopt this flexible approach, allowing learners to use their full linguistic repertoires in discourse creation. This inclusivity reflects a broader understanding of language as social practice and challenges the notion of a single “native-like” standard [Hornberger, 2009, p. 27].

All these developments highlight a paradigm shift in language education: from teaching isolated linguistic forms to cultivating the ability to participate in meaningful discourse. The classroom is now seen as a microcosm of society, where learners engage in authentic communicative acts, negotiate meaning, and develop identities as competent language users. Teachers are not merely transmitters of knowledge but facilitators of discourse, guiding learners through the interactional and cultural dimensions of communication. As Brown [2014, p. 101] observes, effective language instruction integrates linguistic accuracy, social appropriateness, and discourse competence—the three pillars of communicative proficiency.

In conclusion, modern trends in language education are deeply intertwined with the study of discourse. From communicative and task-based learning to technology-enhanced and multilingual approaches, all contemporary innovations reflect the understanding that language is inseparable from its social and cultural contexts. Teaching language today means teaching learners how to interpret, produce, and interact through discourse—how to construct meaning collaboratively, express identity, and engage critically with the world. Ultimately, the goal of modern language education is not merely linguistic fluency but discourse competence: the ability to use language purposefully, appropriately, and effectively in diverse communicative situations.

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TASK-BASED COLLABORATIVE APPROACH IN ESP

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Annotation: This article takes look at the task-based approach to collaboration as a successful way for teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP). The above approach improves the motivation of learners, skills in communication, and capacity to solve problems by incorporating real-world professional challenges into group projects. The research investigation desires to concentrate on the way that collaborative task design, which is instructor facilitation, and peer interaction help learners grasp language in specialized disciplines. It finds that integrating task-based learning (TBL) with collaboration results in genuine learning settings that prepare students for workplace interactions.

Keywords: task-based learning, collaboration, ESP, communicative competence, authentic tasks.

English for certain Purposes (ESP) is designed to provide learners with the language abilities needed in certain professional sectors such as business, medicine, and engineering. One of the most effective techniques to achieving this aim is the task-based collaborative approach, which focusses on accomplishing meaningful tasks through cooperation (Ellis, 2019).

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) allows students to utilise language to achieve real-world communicative goals (Willis & Willis, 2007). When paired with cooperation, TBLT facilitates meaning negotiation, peer feedback, and collaborative issue resolution (Richards 2017). As a result, this study addresses the benefits, problems, and pedagogical consequences of employing a task-based collaborative approach in ESP classes.

1. Principles of Task-Based Collaborative Learning. The task-based collaborative method is founded on the premise that language acquisition is most effective when students engage in projects that mimic real-life conversation (Long, 2015). In ESP, assignments should reflect the learners' work environments. For example, engineering students may create technical papers, but business students may develop marketing strategies as group projects.

According to Nunan (2004), task-based learning emphasises meaning over form, promoting real connection. Collaboration enhances social and cognitive qualities by allowing students to negotiate, plan, and evaluate outcomes together.

2. Designing Effective Collaborative Tasks. ESP learning relies heavily on task design. Teachers should develop activities that are authentic and relevant to real-world professional settings.

Interactive - requires communication among team members;

Goal-oriented means having a particular outcome, such as a report, presentation, or proposal.

For example, medical ESP students can collaborate to develop case studies, whereas IT students can create software project documentation. As Skehan (2016) argues, task complexity and clear objectives encourage deeper processing and improved language creation.

3. Teacher's Role in Task-Based Collaboration. The teacher in this technique serves as a facilitator, guide, and evaluator. Teachers organise group composition, establish time restrictions, and monitor interaction to guarantee equitable participation (Harmer, 2015). Feedback is supplied both during and after the assignment to help with linguistic correctness and fluency.

Teachers should also teach pupils collaboration skills such as negotiating, leadership, and dispute resolution. As Ellis (2019) emphasises, organised direction from teachers ensures that cooperation is constructive and linked with learning objectives.

4. Benefits of the Task-Based Collaborative Approach. Integrating collaboration into task-based learning improves students in a number of ways:

Increased Motivation: When learners feel accountable for the success of the group, they are more engaged (Oxford, 2016).

Improved Communication Skills: Constant engagement increases fluency, pragmatic competence, and vocabulary.

A professional State of readiness: Students practise real-world communication patterns common of their professions.

Empirical research indicates that task-based collaborative learning improves retention, self-confidence, and problem-solving ability.

5. Challenges and Solutions. Despite its benefits, this technique may encounter challenges such as inconsistent participation, a lack of time, or restricted resources. Teachers can address these issues by assigning defined responsibilities, utilising rubrics for group assessments, and using digital collaboration tools such as Google Docs or online forums (Breen, 2018). Proper scaffolding ensures that all students participate equally in the work.

6. Technological Integration. Modern ESP classrooms are increasingly reliant on technology to facilitate communication. Students can conduct synchronous or asynchronous assignments using platforms such as Zoom, Padlet, and Microsoft Teams. These platforms allow for interactivity, document exchange, and continual feedback (Richards, 2017). Virtual cooperation opens up new opportunities for multinational ESP initiatives and cross-cultural communication.

In conclusion, the task-based collaborative method makes for an effective structure to facilitate ESP education. It allows students to practice real professional communication, increases motivation, and develops collaborative skills. By developing meaningful activities and fostering interaction, teachers create an atmosphere in which language is utilized as a genuine instrument for attaining objectives. Future studies should investigate how technology might improve collaborative task execution across several ESP fields.

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COMPARISON OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN URBAN AND RURAL SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article explores the differences in English Language Teaching (ELT) between urban and rural schools in Uzbekistan. The study focuses on the number of teachers, the quality of teaching materials, classroom conditions, and students’ motivation. The research shows that urban schools have better facilities, modern resources, and more qualified teachers, while rural schools face a shortage of teachers, outdated textbooks, and poor classroom conditions. The paper highlights how these differences affect students’ learning outcomes and suggests ways to improve education quality in rural areas.

Keywords: English language teaching, urban education, rural education, teacher shortage, student motivation, Uzbekistan.

Introduction. Education plays a central role in the development of any nation. In Uzbekistan, English is considered one of the most important subjects, as it provides access to global knowledge, communication, and job opportunities. However, there are still large differences in how English is taught in urban and rural schools. Urban schools are located in cities and have better facilities, more teachers, and modern technology. In contrast, rural schools are often under-resourced, with limited teaching materials and a small number of teachers. These inequalities create barriers to equal education for all students. The aim of this research is to compare English teaching in urban and rural schools, identify key challenges, and offer practical recommendations to improve the situation in rural areas. According to Richards and Rodgers (Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching (3rd ed.2014), successful English language learning requires student-centered methods, communicative activities, and access to learning tools such as audio-visual materials [8, 45]. Unfortunately, such resources are often available only in urban schools.

Literature Review. Scholars have long discussed the issue of inequality in education. Akbari and Allvar found that urban teachers have more access to professional development and teaching resources, which improves lesson quality. [1, 1–12] Azimova showed that rural teachers often work alone, have little collaboration, and lack access to training [2, 47]. According to UNESCO (2015), educational differences between rural and urban schools exist in almost every developing country. The main causes are teacher shortages, poor infrastructure, and low salaries [10, 114]. Similarly, Horn and Akiba stated that rural students often have less motivation due to limited opportunities for using English in daily life [5, 15–16]. These studies confirm that social, economic, and geographical factors directly affect English language learning outcomes. In Uzbekistan, the same challenges are present, and this research aims to describe them in a local context.

Methodology. This study uses a comparative qualitative research method. Data was collected from two secondary schools in the Syrdarya region:

- School No. 5 (Gulistan city) – representing an urban area.
- School No. 4 (Gulistan district) – representing a rural area

The research included classroom observation, teacher interviews, and document analysis. Each school's facilities, teacher numbers, and student attitudes were compared. Urban schools had access to modern technology, internet connection, and visual materials, while rural schools relied mainly on traditional teaching methods and textbooks [3, 45–46].

Results and Discussion. 1. Teacher Availability. One of the biggest differences found was in teacher numbers. Urban School No. 5 had more than 10 English teachers who shared responsibilities and organized speaking clubs and competitions. This division of work allowed for smaller classes and more attention to individual students. In contrast, the rural school had only one English teacher for all grades. This teacher had to prepare lessons for multiple levels, handle administrative duties, and teach large mixed-ability classes. As Azimova (2018) mentions, such conditions reduce teaching quality and limit innovation in lessons [2, 47].

2. Learning Environment and Resources. The physical and educational environment also differed significantly. Urban schools were equipped with whiteboards, posters, and multimedia tools such as projectors. Students could borrow English books from the library or use online resources for extra practice. Rural schools, however, had only basic blackboards and outdated textbooks. Internet access was rare, and teachers had no materials to organize group work or interactive activities [1, 6]. Students learned English mostly by memorizing grammar rules, which made lessons less interesting. Akbari and Allvar emphasize that

exposure to authentic materials—such as songs, films, and dialogues—greatly improves learners’ language skills [1, 9]. Lack of such materials in rural schools slows down students’ progress.

3. Student Motivation. Motivation plays an important role in language learning. Urban students are often more motivated because they see English as a valuable skill for future careers or study abroad. They participate in contests, debates, and English clubs, which boost their confidence. In rural schools, students rarely have such opportunities. Most of them study English only to pass exams. Without exposure to English media or communication with fluent speakers, they find it difficult to stay motivated. Lamont also explains that the learning environment strongly shapes students’ attitude toward knowledge; without encouragement, learners tend to lose interest [6, 584–622].

4. Gender and Social Factors. An additional factor found during the research was gender and family influence. In rural areas, some parents believe English is not necessary for everyday life, especially for girls. This social attitude reduces the number of students who aim to continue English learning at higher levels. Meanwhile, in urban families, parents often support their children’s education, paying for private English courses or online lessons. This parental involvement has a strong positive effect on student achievement.

5. Summary of Findings.

Aspect Urban Schools vs Rural Schools

Aspect	Urban school	Rural school
Teachers	10+ qualified teachers	Only one teacher for all grades
Resources	Posters, computers, library, internet	Only textbooks
Class size	Small and divided groups	Large mixed-level group
Motivation	High, supported by clubs	Low, exam-focused
Parental support	Strong	Limited

Conclusion. The findings clearly show that there is a strong urban–rural gap in English teaching conditions in Uzbekistan. Urban schools enjoy better facilities, sufficient teachers, and higher motivation, while rural schools face continuous challenges. To reduce this gap, the following actions are recommended:

1. Provide professional development and training for rural teachers.
2. Increase teacher salaries and incentives to work in remote areas.
3. Ensure equal access to digital tools, books, and modern teaching materials.
4. Encourage community involvement in supporting education.

Improving rural education will not only raise English proficiency but also help build a more equal and educated society. Equal opportunities for all learners are essential for the progress of Uzbekistan’s education system.

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СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИЕ МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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Аннотация: Статья представляет собой результаты исследования специфики основополагающих методических принципов обучения иностранному языку в контексте современной лингвистики и методики.

Ключевые слова: принцип; функция; методика; навык; реализация.

Методические принципы более детально описывают и конкретизируют специфику обучения ИЯ. К этой группе относятся: принцип коммуникативной направленности, учета особенностей родного языка, принцип взаимосвязанного обучения всем видам речевой деятельности, принцип функциональности, устного опережения, аппроксимации, а также целый ряд других принципов, которые формулируются авторами в зависимости от избранного подхода к обучению. Пассов Е.И. рассматривает те из них, которые представляются наиболее важными или наиболее спорными.

1. Принцип устной основы и принцип устного опережения. Принцип устной основы уходит своими корнями в прямой метод. Еще в 1880 г. Ф. Гуэн писал, что устная речь должна предшествовать речи письменной. Это положение было подхвачено американскими неопрямистами и стало одним из базисных в их методике. В чем его суть? Логика рассуждений весьма проста: устная речь появилась раньше письменной, и человек усваивает родной язык сначала в устной форме, а письменная речь есть лишь фиксированная устная речь, следовательно, нужно сначала научиться говорить и понимать, а это уже обеспечит и умение читать, и умение писать. Опираясь на этот принцип, длительное время (от полугода до двух лет) обучают речи на устной основе, т.е. без чтения текстов и без записи. В миниатюре этот подход во многих современных учебниках приобрел вид так называемых устных вводных курсов (от двух недель до четырех месяцев).[1,2] Внедрение принципа устной основы вызывает возражения как теоретического, так и практического характера. Во-первых, большинство людей обладает зрительной и смешанной памятью, а не слуховой. Эффективно ли при этом все основывать на слуховом восприятии? Во-вторых, одним из непреложных положений психологии является следующее: чем больше анализаторов участвует в усвоении, тем оно прочнее. Стоит ли этим пренебрегать? В-третьих, практика показала, что после устных вводных курсов труден переход к чтению и письму.

Методистами, которые руководствовались известным положением И.П. Павлова о ведущей роли речедвигательного анализатора, был выдвинут принцип устного опережения. Он представлялся весьма плодотворным, толкование его, однако, чаще всего не точное. В частности, пишут о том, что при осуществлении этого принципа речь идет лишь об устном введении материала, в основном же все строится на обработке письменных текстов. На практике бывает именно так. Но вряд ли это компрометирует сам принцип. Принцип же предусматривает:

- 1) не просто введение, а автоматизацию определенной дозы речевого материала до того, как приступают к тексту;
- 2) использование текста в качестве зрительного подкрепления и как «содержательной базы» для дальнейшей работы;
- 3) большую работу в устном плане после текста.

Е.И. Пассов считает, что – опережение следует понимать не только и не столько во временном аспекте, как и сколько в количественном: ведь речедвигательный анализатор по значимости – ведущий. Следование этим принципам будет способствовать реализации важнейшей закономерности, согласно которой каждый вид речевой деятельности усваивается главным образом на основе упражнений в этом же виде деятельности.[1,2,3]

2. Принцип комплексности. Считается, что он предполагает совместное усвоение всех четырех видов речевой деятельности. Но просто совместное, параллельное существование видов речевой деятельности – еще не комплексность. Главное в том, чтобы обеспечивалось их взаимовлияние друг на друга при ведущей роли каждого из видов попеременно на разных отрезках процесса обучения.

3. Принцип учета родного языка учащихся. Представители различных методических систем выдвигают разные принципы относительно родного языка обучаемых. Сторонники прямого и натурального методов, например, провозглашают принцип исключения родного языка учащихся из процесса обучения. Другие выдвигают принцип опоры на родной язык, третьи – принцип учета родного языка обучаемых.

Принцип опоры на родной язык предполагает, что на уроке ученику все время необходимо сравнивать формы двух языков, анализировать их сходство и различие с целью детального постижения строя языков. Причем все это направлено на теоретическое осмысление, а не на практическое овладение. Принцип учета родного языка направлен на практическое овладение иноязычной речью. Этому служит, во-первых, такая организация речевого материала, которая способствует предотвращению интерференции со стороны родного языка. Во-вторых, осуществлению принципа способствует соответствующая организация процесса усвоения иноязычных форм (лексических единиц). Данный аспект значим для преподавателя, который обеспечивает профилактику ошибок, предусмотрев их заранее. Таким образом, принцип учета родного языка как бы скрыт от учащегося. Следует отметить, что он может быть эффективно реализован в монойзычной аудитории, в интернациональных же классах, где собраны учащиеся, говорящие на разных языках, учителю сложнее учитывать особенности родного языка всех обучаемых.[1,3]

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TA'LIM JARAYONIGA MUAMMOLI YONDASHUVNING IJTIMOYIY AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayonida muammoli yondashuvning ijtimoiy ahamiyati o‘rganilgan. Muammoli ta'lim usuli o‘quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash, mustaqillik va ijodkorlik kabi muhim ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, muammoli yondashuvning ijtimoiy jihatdan ahamiyati, o‘quvchilarni real hayotdagi muammolarga yo‘naltirish orqali ularning faolligini va ijtimoiy javobgarligini oshirishga hamda ta'lim tizimining samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilganligiga e'tibor qaratilgan. Bu yondashuv, ta'lim jarayonida o‘quvchilarning ma'naviy, intellektual va ijtimoiy taraqqiyotiga hissa qo‘shadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ta'lim jarayoni, muammoli yondashuv, ijtimoiy ahamiyat, tanqidiy fikrlash, mustaqillik, ijodkorlik, ta'lim tizimi, faollik, ijtimoiy javobgarlik, samaradorlik.

Annotation: This article explores the social significance of the problem-based approach in the educational process. The problem-based teaching method aims to develop essential skills such as critical thinking, independence, and creativity in students. Moreover, the article emphasizes that the social importance of this approach lies in guiding students toward real-life problems, increasing their engagement and social responsibility, and enhancing the effectiveness of the education system. This approach contributes to students' moral, intellectual, and social development within the learning process.

Keywords: educational process, problem-based approach, social significance, critical thinking, independence, creativity, education system, engagement, social responsibility, effectiveness.

Аннотация: В данной статье изучается социальная значимость проблемного подхода в образовательном процессе. Метод проблемного обучения направлен на развитие у учащихся таких важных навыков, как критическое мышление, самостоятельность и креативность. Также подчёркивается, что социальная значимость данного подхода заключается в ориентации учащихся на реальные жизненные проблемы, повышении их активности и социальной ответственности, а также в повышении эффективности системы образования. Такой подход способствует духовному, интеллектуальному и социальному развитию учащихся в процессе обучения.

Ключевые слова: образовательный процесс, проблемный подход, социальная значимость, критическое мышление, самостоятельность, креативность, система образования, активность, социальная ответственность, эффективность.

Insoniyat jamiyatining hozirgi zamon rivojlanish darajasi mustaqil respublikamiz ijtimoiy hayotining barcha sohalarida amalga oshirilayotgan tub o'zgarishlarda o'z aksini topmoqda. Bunday o'zgarishlar shak-shubhasiz, barkamol shaxsni tarkib toptirish bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Aynan ana shu masala "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonun va "Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturida o'z aksini topgan. Hozirgi paytda ko'p mamlakatlar, shu jumladan respublikamiz uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida ham turlicha nomlangan texnologiyalardan foydalanilmoqda. Bu texnologiyalarning barchasi ma'lum umumiylikka ega bo'lib, ular xususiy jihatlariga binoan tasniflanishi V. S. Kukushin, G. K. Selevko, G. Berdiyev kabi ko'plab olimlar tomonidan ko'rsatilgan bo'lib, ularni sxematik tarzda keltirish ham mumkin (Individual ta'lim texnologiyasi, Jamoaviy ta'lim texnologiyasi, Belgi-kontekstli ta'lim texnologiyasi, Ishbilarmonlik yoki rolli o'yin ta'lim texnologiyasi, Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasi...).[1,5]

Ana shu vazifalarni hal etishda muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasi yetakchi o'rinni yegallaydi. Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasi juda qadim zamonlardan shakllanib kelmoqda. Jumladan, qadimgi Gretsiyada muammoli savol-javoblar, qadimgi Hindiston va Xitoyda muammoli bahs-munozaralardan keng foydalanilgan. Muammoli ta'limni amerikalik psixolog, faylasuf va pedagog Dj. Dyui 1894 yilda Chikagoda tashkil yetgan tajriba maktabida qo'llagan. XX asrning 30 - yillarida bu yo'nalishda tadqiqotlar olib borildi. 70-80-yillarga kelib, amaliyotga keng joriy etildi.[2,3]

Muammoli ta'lim - bu mantiqiy fikrlash jarayoni (tahlil, umumlashtirish va boshqa shu kabilar) va o'quvchilarning izlanishli faoliyati qonuniyatlarini (muammoli vaziyat, bilishga qiziqish, yehqtiyoj) hisobga olib tuzilgan ta'lim va o'qitishning ilgari ma'lum bo'lgan usullarini qo'llash qoidalarining yangi tizimidir.[4,10]

O'qitish jarayoniga muammoli o'qitish texnologiyasini qo'llash uchun o'qituvchi quyidagi masalalarni hal qilishi lozim:

1. O'quv dasturi bo'yicha mavzularni muammoli dars shaklida o'tish mumkinligini;
2. Mavzu matnidagi masalalar bo'yicha muammoli vaziyatni keltirib chiqaradigan savollar, topshiriqlarni aniqlash, bunda didaktikaning ilmiylik, tizimlilik, mantiqiy ketma-ketlik, izchillik printsiplariga amal qilish;

Muammoli ta'lim o'quvchilarning ijodiy tafakkuri va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini o'stirishda jiddiy ahamiyatga ega. Muammoli ta'limni amaliyotda qo'llashda asosiy masalalardan biri o'rganilayotgan mavzu bilan bog'liq muammoli vaziyat yaratishdan iborat. Muammoli ta'limning asosiy g'oyasi bilimlarni o'quvchilarga tayyor holda berish emas, ular tomonidan dars mavzusiga tegishli muammolar bo'yicha o'quvtadqiqotlarini bajarish asosida o'zlashtirilishini ta'minlashdan iborat.

Demak, muammoli o'qitishni boshqarish pedagogik mahoratni talab etadi, chunki muammoli vaziyatning paydo bo'lishi individual holat bo'lib, tabaqalashtirilgan va individuallashtirilgan yondashuvni talab etadi.[1,9] O'quv materialini muammoli taqdim yetilishining mohiyati shundaki, unda o'qituvchi bilimlarni tayyor holda taqdim etmasdan, o'quvchilar oldiga muammoli masalalar qo'yadi, ularni yechimining yo'llari va vositalarini izlashga undaydi. Muammo, yangi bilimlar va harakat usullar sari, o'zi yo'lga boshlaydi.

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PROBLEMS OF BILINGUAL CONSCIOUSNESS FORMATION

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Annatation: In this article the authors consider the problems of bilingual language consciousness formation. This topic is relevant due to the fact that people can not develop in isolation, and the diversity of languages and their close proximity simply do not leave any choice to man, how to learn foreign languages. The study of other languages allows not only to establish communication and information, but also to enrich the culture of their own people through the introduction of a part of the culture of the people of the studied language.

Keywords: bilingualism, language consciousness, foreign language, language ability.

Today, practical requirements of teaching foreign languages require using “the communicative focused methods, which are directed to formation of abilities adequately to express thoughts in concrete language” [1, p. 60] Moreover, as N. Dauletova states: “Формирование интеллектуального потенциала общества невозможно представить без изучения иностранного языка” [2, p. 87].

Despite of the unambiguity of the term “bilingualism”, we still found some discrepancy. Two types of this phenomena (pure bilingualism and mixed bilingualism) require two types of language acquisition. The first type takes place in the assimilation of the second language “without translation” by its native speakers and, therefore, nationally specific cognitive structures are assimilated, being represented by units of language, without distortion. In case of mixed bilingualism, the studied language is perceived through the prism of the native one. The structure of the studied language is distorted by categories of native language, because there are no absolutely identical concepts among speakers of different languages, moreover, words can denote the same subject, but represent it in different ways, so the translation is never accurate. As N. Nikolina states, “Мышление и речь могут быть рассмотрены только в совокупности” [3, p. 43]. Issues of typology of modern bilingualism are covered in detail in the works of Uzbek and foreign scientists from

different conceptual positions. Thus, one of the most common criteria for identifying types of bilingualism is the level of proficiency in the language code.

According to this parameter, it is common to distinguish the following types:

1) receptive bilingualism (level of perception, understanding and interpretation of the received message);

2) reproductive bilingualism (level of reproduction of what is heard or read);

3) productive bilingualism (level of proficiency in all types of speech activity).

Studying the features of the formation and functioning of cognitive structures in the minds of emerging artificial bilinguals, one should take into account the level of language proficiency. We adhere to the interpretations of the studied phenomena from the standpoint of cognitive linguistics. Within the framework of this scientific paradigm, language consciousness is the property of the individual, so the question of language/speech ability of a person must inevitably be touched upon. We list the basic properties of the language ability of the individual, allocated researchers: the dynamism of language ability, the interaction of developing language ability and speech skills, the complexity of the mechanism of language ability in the emerging linguistic personality.

The problems of bilingual linguistic consciousness formation were considered in the theory of bilingualism, although the term itself was not used by the authors. Thus, we may state that every person, being a native speaker, has a certain set of skills of coding and decoding information in his language. When a person begins to learn a foreign language, he forms new skills of coding and decoding, which come into some interaction with existing ones. When bilinguals move from one language to another, the two systems of coding and decoding skills come into more or less conflict. In this regard, the author considers the concepts of mixed and coordinate bilingualism. According to our theory, a mixed type of bilingualism is characterized by the presence of one common semantic basis for two languages in bilingual consciousness, that is, one system of meanings serves two language codes at once. This type of bilingualism is formed in the process of traditional foreign language teaching, and is typical for children brought up in bilingual families.

Thus, based on the analysis of the concepts of bilingual linguistic consciousness formation proposed by different authors, it can be concluded that the knowledge of a foreign language is carried out through the native language, as a result, a hybrid structure is formed in the consciousness of the subject, represented by the integrated unity of the two pictures of the world.

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INKLYUZIF TA'LIMDA VAQTDAN TO'G'RI FOYDALANISH USULLARI

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Annonatsiya: Bu maqolada Inklyuzif ta'lim jarayonida vaqt taqsimoti, undan unumli foydalanish hamda vaqtdan to'g'ri foydalanish usullari haqida yozilgan. Buyuk allomalarimiz so'zlari Vaqt oqar daryo u hech qachon to'xtab turmaydi. Mavzuga oid xalqaro tajribalar chet el olimlarining vaqtdan unumli foydalanish samaraga olib kelish haqidagi amaliyot va nazariyalari.

Kalit so'zlar: Vaqt, inklyuzif talim, xalqaro tajriba, samaradorlik, vaqt qadri, ulug' nemat, menejer, reja, fikrlash.

Abstract: This article discusses time allocation in the process of inclusive education, effective use of time, and methods for managing it efficiently. The sayings of great scholars emphasize that "time is like a flowing river - it never stops." The article also explores international experiences, including the practices and theories of foreign researchers on how the effective use of time leads to success.

Keywords: time, inclusive education, international experience, efficiency, value of time, precious blessing, manager, planning, thinking.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы распределения времени в процессе инклюзивного образования, эффективного использования времени и методы рационального управления им. Великие мыслители говорили: «Время - как текущая река, оно никогда не останавливается». В статье также анализируется международный опыт, а также практики и теории зарубежных учёных о том, как рациональное использование времени способствует достижению успеха.

Ключевые слова: время, инклюзивное образование, международный опыт, эффективность, ценность времени, великая благодать, менеджер, планирование, мышление.

Amerikalik sotsiolog J. Koulman tomonidan taklif etilgan oqilona tanlov nazariyasi ijtimoiy fikrlashning tobora ommalashgan variantiga aylanib bormoqda. U tizimning tushunchalarini rad etadi. Resurs tushunchalari va safarbarlik masalalariga e'tibor qaratiladi. M. Kroze bilan birgalikda J. Koulman tashkilot ichida ijtimoiy harakatlar nazariyasini ishlab chiqdi va qarorlarni qabul qilish jarayonini o'rganish va samaradorligini aniqlashda g'oyalarni emas, balki turli strategiyalarning muhimligini ta'kidladi. Bu vaqtni samarali tashkil etish tizimini o'rganish evolyutsiyasi bilan bog'liq. Batafsil o'ziga xoslik uchun "menejment" atamasi (hozirgi ma'noda - ilmiy asoslangan professional boshqaruv faoliyati) va "time management" (vaqtni boshqarish bo'yicha menejer qobiliyatlari) ning barqaror terminologik birikmasi paydo bo'lgandan beri g'oyani ko'rib chiqish kerak.

Vaqtni boshqarishning uch bosqichi mavjud. G'arbda olimlar o'z ishlarida xodimning aqliy mehnati emas, balki jismoniy samaradorligiga e'tibor berishadi. Agar biz xodimlarga bo'lgan munosabatning umumiy moyilligini ajratib olishga harakat qilsak, u holda xodim passiv ob'ekt deb hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, Teylor ishni tez va samaradorligi bo'yicha xodimga asossiz talablar qo'yadigan ishni tashkil qilishning "terlash tizimlari" ni tanqid qilgan. Teylorning aytishicha, "terlash 39 tizimlari" va "tabiiy dangasalik" o'rtasidagi "oltin o'rliq", vaqtni boshqarish kabi muhim sohani o'zida mujassam etgan ilmiy ishlab chiqarishni boshqarish usullarida aniqlanadi. Taylor, A.Fayol, G.Ford, F. va L.Gilbret, G.Gant, G.Emerson va boshqa mashhur shaxslarning asosiy maqsadi – zamonaviy tashkilotlarning faoliyatida foydalanilishi mumkin bo'lgan unumdorlikni oshirishning asosiy tamoyillarini shakllantirishdan va shuningdek menejerlar va mutaxassislarining shaxsiy samaradorligini oshirishdan iborat. Shunday qilib, menejmentni boshqarish darajasida xodimlarning shaxsiy samaradorligi muammolarini ko'rib chiqish zarurligi haqidagi g'oyani ta'kidlagan ilmiy boshqaruv maktabining klassikasiga yaqinlashishi aqliy, ijodiy va boshqaruv mehnatining nisbati ortib borayotgan vaqtda bizning davrimizga tegishli deb hisoblanishi mumkin. Vaqt –

qadri ulug' ne'mat. Vaqt haqida, uning qadr-qimmati, undan unumli foydalanishimiz lozimligi haqida milliy ma'naviy merosimizda, islom dinida ham fikrlar bildiriladi. Vaqt – go'yo hayot kiyimi to'qiladigan iplar bo'lib, uning pishiq va nafisligiga qarab hayot aziz va bebaho bo'ladi. Agar iplar yomon va to'zigan bo'lsa hayot ham tuban, bema'no va mazmunsiz bo'ladi. Vaqtning yana bir xususiyati agar u o'tib ketsa, qaytib kelmaydi. Vaqt inson sarf qiladigan asosiy dastamoyasidir. U qanchalik ko'p bo'lsa ham ozdir. Oz bo'lsayu barakali bo'lsa, u ko'pdir. Inson o'z hayotining har bir daqiqa va lahzasidan unumli va barakali foydalanib, uni yaxshi amallar qilishga sarflashi lozimdir. Shunda u Hazarati Payg'ambarimiz Muhammad (s.a.v) marhamat qilib aytgan hadisi shariflari mazmuniga muvofiq ish tutgan bo'ladi. Rasuliakram (s.a.v) dedilar: "Qiyomat kunida bandaning qadami to to'rt narsadan so'ralmaguncha joyidan jilmaydi; umrini qanday o'tkazgani, yoshligida nima qilgani, molini qaerdan topib nimaga sarf qilgani, ilmiga qay darajada amal qilgani haqida" – deyiladi. Islom ta'limoti yalqovlik, loqaydlik, beparvolik kabi ijtimoiy illatlardan uzoqda bo'lishga, undan panohtilashga amr qiladi va har vaqt har kuni erta turib, xayrli amallarni qilishga, hamda yoshlik, sihat-salomatlik, boylik, bo'sh vaqt va dunyo hayotini g'animat bilishga chorlaydi. Imom atTermiziy rivoyat qilgan ushbu xadisda Rasululloh s.a.v nasihat kilib: "Besh narsani besh narsadan oldin g'animat biling: keksalikdan oldin yoshlikni, betoblikdan oldin salomatlikni, faqirlikdan oldin boylikni, bandlikdan oldin bo'sh vaqtningni, o'limingdan oldin tiriklikni g'animat biling". –dedilar. Ulug' ajdodlarimiz kunlarini, vaqtu soatlarini foydali ish qilishga, go'zal ahloqiy va ilmiy darajalarga etishish yo'lida sarf qilishda doim ogoh va sergak edilar. Shuning uchun ham ularning bugunlari kechagisidan, ertangi kunlari bugungisidan a'lo va afzal bo'lardi. Ular: "Vaqt qilichdir, agar sen uni kesmasang u seni kesadi" –degan hikmatli so'zga amal qilishgan. Har birimiz o'tayotgan kunimiz, vaqtimizdan ibrat olmog'imiz lozim. Zero, kecha va kunduz yangilarni eskirtiradi, uzoqlarni yaqin qiladi, umrlarni qisqartiradi, yoshlarni qaritadi, keksalarni foniylilik sari etaklaydi.

Donishmandlardan biri shunday deydi: "Kim kunini bekorga o'tkazsa, bir yaxshi amalni qilmasa, insonlarga chiroyli so'z yoki yaxshi muomala qilmasa, bir ilmu ma'rifat hosil qilmasa, u kuniga jabr qilib, o'ziga zulm qilibdi". Dono xalqimizda bir maqol bor, unda shunday deyiladi: "Vaqtning ketdi, baxting ketdi". Ha, vaqt go'yo ulug' baxt kabidir, uni g'animat bilmaslik katta gunohdir: Kunlar, vaqtlar tinmay o'tsa-yu, qaytib kelmas daqiqalarimizga beparvo bo'lsak, bundan pandu-nasihat olmasak, ikki dunyo saodatiga aslo musharraf bo'la olmaymiz. Albatta, oqilu donishmand inson atrofga ibrat nazari bilan boqadi, dunyoda kechayotgan hodisa va o'zgarishlarga, oltindan qimmatli vaqtningni qadrlash zarurligini qalbida tasdiqlaydi va shunga muvofiq ish tutadi. Ulug' piru murshidlardan biri Bahouddin Naqshband hazratlari bunday deb marhamat qilganlar: "Kim vaqtini zoe ketkazsa, vaqt uning dushmaniga aylanadi, nafasning zoe bo'lishiga yo'l qo'ymang va undan ehtiyot bo'ling". Donishmandlardan biri aytganidek, biz uchun umrimiz necha kundan iboratligi emas, balki bugungi kunimizda, ayni lahzalarda qanday yashay olishimiz muhim. Zero, ulug'lar aytganidek, odamzot hayoti tejalgan vaqtga qarab uzayadi. Jamiyatimizdagi barcha insonlar, ular kim va qanday mavqega ega bo'lmasinlar, ayniqsa, kelajagimiz bo'lgan yoshlarimiz, aziz farzandlarimiz oltindan qimmat vaqt va undan unumli foydalanish va uni g'animat bilishi lozimdir. Buning uchun har bir kishi hayotdagi mas'uliyatini 40 chuqur anglagan holda ish tutmog'i zarur bo'ladi. Shuning uchun yoshi ulug' keksalarimiz, muhtaram ota-onalar farzandlarimiz ta'lim-tarbiyasiga beparvo bo'lmasligimiz, ularni o'z vaqtlarini to'g'ri, solih foydali amallar qilishga sarflashni o'rgatishimiz kerak. Oqil kishi vaqtga beparvo bo'lishi mutlaqo mumkin emas. Xasis odam mol-dunyoga ziqna bo'lganidek, dono kishi ham vaqti bekor ketishiga rozi bo'lmasligi kerak. Inson ba'zan o'zi yashab o'tkazgan hayotga qaraydi. Hayoti boshlangan soatdan xisoblab, shuncha yil, shuncha kun yashabman-a, deydi. Lekin bu

muddat unga bir kun o'tganga ham o'xshamaydi. Inson bu haqiqatni shu dunyoning o'zidayoq his etmoqda.

Inklyuziv ta'limda vaqtdan to'g'ri foydalanish – bu o'qituvchidan professional mahorat, rejalashtirish qobiliyati, innovatsion yondashuv va hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini talab etadigan murakkab vazifadir. Ushbu usullarni qo'llash orqali biz har bir o'quvchining, shu jumladan, maxsus ta'limga muhtoj bolalarning ham sifatli ta'lim olishini ta'minlashga erishamiz. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, inklyuziv jamiyat qurish yo'lida muhim qadam bo'ladi.

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THE USE OF ONLINE TOOLS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article explores the use of online tools in developing students' speaking skills in Uzbekistan. It highlights effective language learning methods through digital tools such as AI-powered chatbots, Promova, Kahoot and Quizlet. The study emphasizes how online technology enhances English communication, learner motivation, and interactive speaking practice in modern education. Some scientists believe that combining structured learning with immersive experiences leads to better fluency and retention [4].

Keywords: Language learning, English, methods, AI-powered chatbot, Promova, Quizlet, Kahoot online technologies, digital tools.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston talabalari og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda onlayn vositalardan foydalanish tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda AI asosidagi chat-botlar, Promova, Kahoot va Quizlet kabi raqamli vositalar orqali samarali til o'rganish usullari yoritiladi. Onlayn texnologiyalar ingliz tili kommunikatsiyasi, o'quvchilar motivatsiyasi va interaktiv nutq amaliyotini yaxshilashi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til o'rganish, ingliz tili, usullar, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi chat-bot, Promova, Quizlet, Kahoot, onlayn texnologiyalar, raqamli vositalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается использование онлайн-инструментов для развития навыков говорения у студентов Узбекистана. Исследование

подчеркивает эффективные методы изучения языка с помощью цифровых средств, таких как чат-боты на основе искусственного интеллекта, Promova, Kahoot и Quizlet. Отмечается, что онлайн-технологии способствуют улучшению английской коммуникации, мотивации учащихся и интерактивной практики устной речи.

Ключевые слова: Изучение языка, английский язык, методы, чат-бот на основе искусственного интеллекта, Promova, Quizlet, Kahoot, онлайн-технологии, цифровые инструменты.

English is an essential language for global communication, business, and education. Despite its importance, many learners struggle with fluency due to time constraints, lack of motivation, and ineffective learning methods. Traditional classroom instruction often focuses heavily on grammar and vocabulary without providing enough real-world application. This can result in learners memorizing rules without developing speaking and comprehension skills.

One of the most effective ways for Uzbek students at secondary schools to learn English is through the use, where learners surround themselves with the language in everyday situations. Watching English movies, listening to music, and engaging with native speakers naturally enhances language skills. Studies have shown that students in immersion programs consistently outperform traditional learners in both comprehension and speaking abilities. Language exchange programs and online conversation platforms offer valuable speaking opportunities, making immersion more accessible for students who do not live in English-speaking environments [7].

The digital age has revolutionized language learning. Apps like Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone offer gamified experiences, while online courses on platforms like Coursera, BBC Learning English provide structured learning paths. These digital resources offer flexibility, allowing learners to practice at their own pace. Furthermore, AI-powered chatbots and virtual tutors have become increasingly effective in simulating real-life conversations [3].

Reading is fundamental to language acquisition. Books, newspapers, and online articles provide exposure to diverse vocabulary and writing styles. Beginners can start with graded readers, which simplify language while maintaining engaging storylines. Extensive reading has been linked to faster vocabulary retention and improved grammar acquisition. Interactive e-books, which include built-in definitions and pronunciation guides, further enhance comprehension. Research indicates that learners who engage in daily reading demonstrate higher retention rates and stronger contextual understanding.

Listening to podcasts, audiobooks, and Promova improves comprehension skills. Studies suggest that learners who engage with native speaker content develop better pronunciation and contextual understanding. The shadowing technique widely used by Uzbek learners while repeating spoken words immediately after hearing them has been found to significantly enhance pronunciation accuracy [8]. Watching movies without subtitles also strengthens the students' listening comprehension by forcing the learners to grasp meaning from context. Furthermore, exposure to various English accents (e.g., British, American, Australian) helps the learners adapt to different speech patterns, making real-world conversations easier to follow.

Setting clear, achievable goals helps maintain motivation. The SMART goal framework (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) is an effective way to track progress [6]. For example, instead of a vague goal like "improve English," the learners can set specific targets such as "learn 10 new words daily" or "hold a five-minute conversation in English by the end of the month". [5].

Speaking is often the most challenging skill to develop among Uzbek learners. They admit that language partners, online conversation platforms, and role-playing exercises improve fluency. Other students claim that practicing with native speakers or advanced learners accelerates progress. However, the main role belongs to the learners who practice speaking at least three times a week develop better fluency and confidence [1]. Almost the same amount of university students states the fact that recording and listening to one's own speech helps identify areas for their improvement. Additionally, debate clubs and discussion groups provide structured speaking opportunities that reinforce conversational skills. Even talking to oneself in English has been found to be an effective technique for reinforcing sentence structure and pronunciation.

A rich vocabulary is essential for effective communication. Learning words in context, rather than in isolation, helps with retention. Flashcards, spaced repetition systems (SRS), and mnemonic techniques are particularly effective for vocabulary building. Apps like Kahoot and Quizlet help learners retain new words by reinforcing them at strategic intervals. Additionally, word association techniques, such as linking a new word to a familiar concept, enhance recall. Research suggests that students using spaced repetition techniques retain new vocabulary more effectively than those relying on rote memorization [2].

Mastering English requires a combination of immersion, technology, structured reading, active listening, goal-setting, and conversation practice. Research-based strategies and consistent effort lead to significant improvements in fluency. By addressing common challenges such as lack of motivation and fear of making mistakes, learners can create a personalized learning routine that fits their needs. Studies confirm that students who integrate immersive techniques into their daily routines achieve greater fluency and confidence compared to those who rely solely on classroom instruction. With determination and the right resources, achieving fluency in English is an attainable goal.

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DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE PUBLIC SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article explores the fundamental strategies for developing public speaking competence and confidence. It outlines the essential components of effective speeches, including strong openings, audience awareness, confident body language, and methods to manage stage fright. The study emphasizes that public speaking is not an innate ability but a skill that can be improved through deliberate practice, preparation, and self-

reflection. The article also analyzes practical techniques such as voice control, the use of pauses, and visual engagement with the audience.

Keywords: public speaking, confidence, body language, audience, communication, presentation skills

Public speaking is one of the most valuable and transferable skills in education, business, and everyday life, as it goes beyond merely speaking in front of an audience to encompass the ability to connect, inspire, and communicate ideas clearly and persuasively (Lucas, 2020). Whether addressing classmates, presenting research, or delivering a professional talk, effective public speaking builds confidence, strengthens leadership qualities, and enhances overall communication competence. In today's digital era, public speaking also extends to virtual presentations and online platforms, where mastering tone, camera presence, and visual design is equally important for maintaining audience engagement. However, many individuals experience anxiety, stage fright, or a lack of structure when speaking publicly (Daly et al., 2019). This anxiety often stems from fear of judgment, negative evaluation, or forgetting one's message. To become an effective speaker, it is essential to master key components such as creating a strong and engaging beginning, using confident body language and appearance, adapting to diverse audiences, and developing confidence through preparation and self-awareness.

A strong introduction captures the audience's attention, establishes credibility, and introduces the topic clearly and appealingly (Carnegie, 2019). Using hooks-such as a question, quote, or story-creates emotional engagement, while strategic pauses allow listeners to process information and help the speaker manage nervousness (Gallo, 2014). Successful speakers often open with personal anecdotes or relatable scenarios to build an emotional bridge with the audience. The use of rhetorical devices such as repetition, metaphors, and parallelism can also make speeches more memorable and persuasive. Moreover, pacing and vocal variation-modifying tone, pitch, and volume-add liveliness and clarity, preventing monotony and sustaining audience interest. Non-verbal communication, including posture, gestures, facial expressions, and appearance, significantly influences how messages are received, as confident and open body language conveys sincerity, authority, and trustworthiness (Mehrabian, 2017). The audience's first impression often forms within seconds, making posture, attire, and composure crucial. Eye contact fosters trust and inclusivity, while purposeful gestures strengthen the meaning of words. In cross-cultural contexts, speakers must remain aware that gestures and expressions can vary in meaning; therefore, cultural sensitivity is key (Neuliep, 2020). Additionally, environmental awareness-how the speaker uses space, stage movement, or proximity-can help emphasize ideas and create a dynamic interaction with the audience.

Understanding audience diversity is another cornerstone of effective communication. Audiences differ not only in age, culture, and language but also in communication preferences and expectations. Research by Erikson (2019) classifies people into four personality types-red (goal-oriented), yellow (social and expressive), blue (analytical and detail-oriented), and green (supportive and calm). Recognizing these differences allows speakers to tailor tone, examples, and humor appropriately. For instance, using stories and humor might appeal to expressive audiences, while data and evidence may resonate more with analytical listeners. Effective speakers adjust their content and delivery style to meet these varied needs, ensuring inclusivity and understanding (Beebe & Beebe, 2018).

Confidence, a crucial factor in public speaking, develops through consistent practice, rehearsal, and visualization. Stage fright can be managed by thorough preparation-organizing

content logically, anticipating questions, and familiarizing oneself with the setting. Rehearsing multiple times, recording speeches, or practicing in front of a mirror improves delivery, pronunciation, and timing (Lucas, 2020). Visualization and mindfulness techniques, such as deep breathing or meditation, help control anxiety and promote mental focus (Cuddy, 2015). Additionally, maintaining healthy habits-adequate sleep, hydration, and controlled caffeine intake-positively affects vocal quality and energy levels. Joining speaking clubs such as Toastmasters International or engaging in debate societies can provide structured opportunities for improvement through feedback and peer support.

Ultimately, public speaking is not an innate talent but a learned skill cultivated through preparation, persistence, and reflection. Effective speakers use a combination of verbal and non-verbal strategies-voice modulation, pauses, gestures, storytelling, and visual aids-to build meaningful connections with audiences. In modern contexts, technology-enhanced speaking-such as using multimedia slides, videos, or infographics-can further engage listeners when used thoughtfully. Through these techniques, speakers can inform, inspire, and influence others, bridging the gap between knowledge and impact. As many communication scholars affirm, excellence in public speaking emerges not from natural ability but from dedication, awareness, and experience (Carnegie, 2019; Gallo, 2014; Lucas, 2020). In essence, every speech is an opportunity to lead, educate, and connect-turning words into a powerful tool for change and human connection.

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EXPLORING LINGUISTIC BLENDING IN UZBEK EFL CONTEXTS

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Abstract. This paper explores the phenomenon of language mixing in Uzbek EFL classrooms, focusing on why and how students blend Uzbek and English during lessons. Drawing from classroom observations and previous studies, it argues that code-mixing is not necessarily a sign of linguistic weakness but often a communicative strategy that aids comprehension and expression. The paper further discusses the cultural and pedagogical dimensions of language mixing and proposes practical methods for teachers to manage it effectively while maintaining English immersion.

Keywords: Language mixing, EFL classrooms, code-switching, Uzbek learners, bilingual education, language pedagogy.

Introduction: In recent years, English education in Uzbekistan has expanded rapidly, with students starting to learn English as early as primary school. However, a common phenomenon observed in classrooms is the mixing of Uzbek and English - often referred to as *code-mixing* or *code-switching*. Teachers frequently encounter students who say sentences like “Teacher, bu word nimani anglatadi?” or “Men homeworkni qildim but I’m not sure if it’s correct.” Such examples reflect how natural language blending has become in EFL settings. Understanding this phenomenon is vital for improving classroom communication and developing culturally responsive teaching practices [1].

Language mixing, also known as *code-switching*, is a common phenomenon in multilingual environments where speakers alternate between two or more languages in communication. In Uzbekistan, where Uzbek is the native language and English is learned as a foreign language, language mixing often occurs naturally in classrooms. Students tend to insert Uzbek words or phrases into English sentences to express concepts they cannot yet articulate in English. This helps them maintain fluency in speech and reduce communication anxiety. For example, a learner might say, “Teacher, today we have “*imtihon*,” replacing the English word “exam” with the Uzbek equivalent. Such patterns are not merely linguistic errors but reflect a developing bilingual competence where both linguistic systems coexist and support each other. [2].

Teachers in Uzbek EFL classrooms often employ language mixing not out of weakness but as a conscious pedagogical choice. In classes where students share the same mother tongue, strategic use of Uzbek helps bridge the gap between known and unknown concepts. For example, when introducing abstract grammar like “conditional sentences” or idiomatic expressions, teachers may explain in Uzbek first, then reinforce the concept in English. This bilingual scaffolding builds a strong foundation for deeper understanding. Moreover, language mixing helps maintain lesson flow and reduces confusion, especially when students struggle to follow long English instructions. Another important factor is time efficiency. Explaining complex terms entirely in English can be time-consuming, particularly for lower-level learners. A brief switch to Uzbek clarifies meaning immediately, ensuring that all students progress together [3].

From a sociolinguistic perspective, language mixing in Uzbek EFL classrooms reflects the intersection of identity, culture, and communication. Many Uzbek learners perceive English as a symbol of modernity and opportunity, while Uzbek represents familiarity, emotion, and solidarity. By alternating between the two, students express both their cultural belonging and their aspiration for global connection. In peer conversations, language mixing often signals group membership or humor. Psychologically, this phenomenon can be interpreted through Krashen’s “Affective Filter Hypothesis,” which suggests that emotional comfort enhances language acquisition. When learners are permitted to express themselves in both languages, they feel less anxious and more willing to experiment with English. Code-switching also fosters peer collaboration - weaker students receive help from stronger peers through explanations in Uzbek, reinforcing comprehension for both sides. Rather than being a sign of deficiency, language mixing becomes a strategy for managing cognitive load and emotional balance during learning [4].

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CURRENT ISSUES AND SOLUTIONS IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta’lim tizimining rivojlanishi, unda yuzaga keladigan asosiy muammolar va ularni hal qilish yo’llari tahlil qilinadi. Unda ta’lim sifatiga ta’sir etuvchi omillar, o’qituvchilarning roli va innovatsion yondashuvlarning ahamiyati o’rganiladi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada o’qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish, o’quvchilar motivatsiyasini oshirish, o’quv jarayoni samaradorligini ta’minlash bo’yicha ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: ta’lim tizimi, o’qitish jarayoni, innovatsion texnologiya, motivatsiya, malaka, ta’lim sifati, zamonaviy pedagogika.

Abstract: This article analyzes the development of the modern education system, the key problems that arise within it, and possible solutions. It explores factors affecting the quality of education, the role of teachers, and the importance of innovative approaches. In addition, the article provides scientifically grounded recommendations for using modern technologies in teaching, enhancing student motivation, and ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process.

Key words: education system, teaching process, innovative technology, motivation, qualification, quality of education, modern pedagogy.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется развитие современной системы образования, основные проблемы, возникающие в ней, и пути их решения. Рассматриваются факторы, влияющие на качество образования, роль педагогов и значение инновационных подходов. Кроме того, в статье даны научно обоснованные рекомендации по использованию современных технологий в обучении, повышению мотивации учащихся и обеспечению эффективности образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: система образования, процесс обучения, инновационные технологии, мотивация, квалификация, качество образования, современная педагогика.

In today’s era of globalization and information technology, the education system has become one of the key factors determining the level of a society’s development. The rapid advancement of digital tools, technology, and communication means has brought significant transformation to the teaching and learning process. In this context, the modern teacher is

expected not only to impart knowledge but also to nurture creative, independent, and responsible thinkers capable of critical analysis and problem-solving.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has emphasized: “Educating our youth to become individuals who have mastered modern knowledge and professions and who can think independently is our main task.” This statement clearly highlights the urgent need to improve the quality, content, and methodology of today’s education system.

There are several pressing issues in the modern educational process, most of which are connected with the quality, content, and methodology of teaching. One of the main problems is the uneven quality of education between urban and rural schools. Differences in infrastructure, teacher qualifications, and technical resources affect the overall effectiveness of the learning process.

Another significant issue lies in the dominance of traditional teaching methods. Many teachers still rely on lecture-based, passive methods that limit students’ engagement in learning activities. As a result, learners become passive listeners rather than active participants, which weakens the development of critical thinking, creativity, and analytical skills.

A further problem is the low level of student motivation. Repetitive, unengaging lessons and assessment systems based solely on theoretical knowledge reduce students’ interest and participation. At the same time, the limited use of modern information technologies remains a major challenge. In many educational institutions, especially in remote areas, digital tools, online platforms, and multimedia resources are not yet fully integrated into the learning process.

To overcome these challenges, it is essential to implement comprehensive reforms aimed at improving the quality and effectiveness of teaching. The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies plays a crucial role in this regard. Methods such as Blended Learning, Flipped Classroom, and Project-Based Learning can make lessons more interactive, engaging, and student-centered.

Continuous professional development of teachers is also a key factor in modern education. Through seminars, workshops, and online training courses, teachers can master new methodologies, exchange experiences, and enhance their creative teaching skills. In addition, updating curricula and textbooks according to modern requirements and increasing the share of practical lessons can significantly strengthen students’ real-life skills and creative thinking.

Another important direction is increasing students’ motivation. The use of gamification, competitive tasks, and project-based activities fosters active participation and curiosity. A reward-based assessment system can also encourage students’ confidence and engagement in the learning process.

Furthermore, the development of digital education is one of the most urgent needs of the present time. The use of online learning platforms, distance education systems, virtual laboratories, artificial intelligence, and digital libraries can significantly improve the accessibility and quality of education, especially for learners in remote regions.

When these approaches are successfully implemented, students develop the ability to think independently, analyze critically, and express creativity in various contexts. Teachers, in turn, become lifelong learners-innovative professionals who are open to change and capable of applying advanced pedagogical strategies in practice. Consequently, the education system becomes more effective, modern, and compatible with global standards.

In summary, the modernization of the educational process is one of the key priorities of today’s society. Solving issues such as uneven education quality, low motivation, and

limited use of technology requires innovative approaches. The implementation of modern teaching methods, digital tools, and continuous teacher development can significantly improve the effectiveness of education. As a result, the education system will form a new generation of creative, independent, and globally competent individuals.

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THE INTEGRATIVE-REFLECTIVE APPROACH TO DEVELOPING DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Annotation: The article argues that the Integrative-Reflective Approach provides a powerful methodological foundation for developing teacher and teaching competency effectively. By synthesizing theoretical knowledge with practical application and embedding continuous critical reflection, this approach facilitates a transformative professional learning process. Drawing on international theory and domestic research from Uzbekistan, this article explores the pedagogical foundations of this approach, delineates its role in constructing teachers' DI skills, and positions it as a vital catalyst for achieving modern educational objectives, particularly within the context of ongoing educational reforms.

Keywords: differentiated instruction, integrative-reflective approach, teacher professional development, reflective practice, English language teaching, competency-based education.

The paradigm of education is shifting globally from a teacher-centered, transmission model to a student-centered, constructivist one. This shift is driven by the recognition that learners possess varied readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles [7]. Nowhere is this diversity more palpable than in the language classroom, where students must develop a complex interplay of communicative, grammatical, and sociolinguistic competencies. Differentiated Instruction (DI) stands as a pedagogical imperative in this context, offering a

philosophy and practice of teaching that proactively plans for and responds to learner variance.

However, a significant challenge persists in teacher professional development: the "knowing-doing gap." Teachers may understand the principles of DI theoretically yet struggle to integrate them fluidly and effectively into their daily practice. This suggests that conventional, top-down training models are insufficient for fostering the deep, nuanced competency that DI requires. We posit that closing this gap requires an approach that is itself differentiated for the learner-the teacher.

This article proposes the Integrative-Reflective Approach as a robust framework for teacher professional development, one that transitions educators from being passive recipients of knowledge to becoming active, analytical, and adaptive architects of their own practice. By examining its theoretical underpinnings, pedagogical applications, and specific relevance to the Uzbek educational context, we will demonstrate how this approach is essential for cultivating the professional competence of English language teachers.

The efficacy of the Integrative-Reflective Approach lies in the synergistic relationship between its two core components: integrative learning and reflective practice. These are not separate strands but are interwoven to create a strong foundation for professional growth.

Integration serves as the horizontal dimension of the approach, focusing on the synthesis of knowledge and skills. In the context of DI, this means moving beyond isolated strategies to create a cohesive professional understanding. Firstly, it involves the crucial theory-practice integration. Teachers must connect the models of scholars like Tomlinson and the psychological foundations of Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development to the real-world dynamics of their own classrooms [8]. Secondly, it demands cross-disciplinary integration, encouraging teachers to draw on insights from neuroscience about learning processes, technology for creating flexible learning materials, and classroom management strategies to support a differentiated environment. This holistic view prevents DI from being reduced to a simple bag of tricks and instead frames it as a comprehensive, interconnected philosophy of teaching.

Reflective practice, the vertical dimension, provides the depth for this integrative breadth. Rooted in the seminal work of Donald Schön, reflection is the mechanism that transforms experience into expertise [5]. Schön's concepts of reflection-in-action (the ability to think and adapt in the moment) and reflection-on-action (the systematic analysis of practice after the event) are directly applicable to the dynamic, improvisational nature of differentiated teaching. When a teacher attempts to tier an activity for varied proficiency levels, they are engaging in reflection-in-action; when they later analyze student work products to refine that activity for future use, they are engaged in reflection-on-action. This cyclical process aligns perfectly with the principles of andragogy [2], which posit that adult learners are self-directed, experience-rich, and motivated by learning they perceive as relevant to their real-life challenges. For the practicing teacher, reflection is the tool that connects new DI strategies to their existing reservoir of classroom experience, making the learning personally meaningful and professionally sustainable.

The ultimate significance of the Integrative-Reflective Approach lies in its capacity to foster professional autonomy and align with broader educational objectives. By prioritizing reflection and the integration of personal experience, the approach cultivates what Carol Dweck (2006) would term a "growth mindset" in teachers. Challenges in implementing DI are reframed from being insurmountable obstacles to being opportunities for learning and innovation. This empowerment is crucial, as it transforms teachers from technicians merely

implementing prescribed methods into reflective practitioners capable of making informed, context-sensitive pedagogical judgments.

This transformation is particularly salient within the context of educational reforms in Uzbekistan. National strategic documents, such as the "Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2036" and the "Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030," explicitly call for a modernization of teaching practices, a shift to student-centered learning, and a significant enhancement of teacher quality. Domestic scholars have begun to lay the groundwork for this shift.

For example, Sobirowa specifically highlights the unique features and necessities of a differentiated approach in foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan [6], while Ochil [3] and Rakhmonova [4] explore the value of differentiated and reflective models in teacher preparation.

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TA'LIM - JAMIYAT TARAQQIYOTINING ASOSI

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Annotatsiya: Har bir jamiyatning rivojlanish darajasi, avvalo, uning ta'lim tizimiga berilgan e'tibor bilan belgilanadi. Zamonaviy dunyoda ta'lim - nafaqat shaxsiy taraqqiyot, balki ijtimoiy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy yuksalishning eng muhim omilidir. Chunki bilimli avlod kelajakning kafolati sanaladi. Insonning dunyoqarashi, ijtimoiy faolligi, kasbiy malakasi va tafakkuri aynan ta'lim orqali shakllanadi. Bugungi globallashuv va raqobatbardoshlik davrida har bir davlat zamonaviy bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga intilmoqda. Bu esa jamiyatda bilimli, mustaqil fikrlaydigan, innovatsion g'oyalarga boy shaxslar shakllanishiga zamin yaratadi. Ta'lim tizimi kuchli bo'lgan jamiyatda ijtimoiy barqarorlik, madaniy yuksalish va iqtisodiy farovonlik yuqori bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tizimi, inson kapitali, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, ijtimoiy barqarorlik, innovatsiya, raqamli texnologiyalar, globallashuv, kadrlar tayyorlash, ta'lim islohotlari, zamonaviy pedagogika, STEAM yondashuvi, sun'iy intellekt, raqobatbardoshlik, barqaror taraqqiyot, ma'naviy qadriyatlar.

Annotation: The level of development of any society is primarily determined by the attention given to its education system. In the modern world, education is not only a means of personal development but also a crucial factor in social, political, and economic advancement. An educated generation is regarded as the guarantee of the future. A person's worldview, social activity, professional competence, and intellect are all shaped through education. In today's era of globalization and competitiveness, every nation strives to train specialists equipped with modern knowledge and skills. This, in turn, fosters the formation of knowledgeable, independent, and innovative individuals. In a society with a strong education system, social stability, cultural progress, and economic prosperity are significantly higher.

Key words: education system, human capital, economic development, social stability, innovation, digital technologies, globalization, professional training, educational reforms, modern pedagogy, STEAM approach, artificial intelligence, competitiveness, sustainable development, moral values.

Аннотация: Уровень развития любого общества определяется, прежде всего, вниманием, уделяемым системе образования. В современном мире образование - это не только средство личностного развития, но и важнейший фактор социального, политического и экономического прогресса. Образованное поколение считается залогом будущего. Мировоззрение человека, его социальная активность, профессиональная компетентность и мышление формируются именно через образование. В эпоху глобализации и конкуренции каждое государство стремится готовить специалистов, обладающих современными знаниями и навыками. Это создает основу для формирования образованных, самостоятельных и инновационно мыслящих личностей. В обществе с сильной системой образования выше уровень социальной стабильности, культурного развития и экономического благополучия.

Ключевые слова: система образования, человеческий капитал, экономическое развитие, социальная стабильность, инновации, цифровые технологии, глобализация, подготовка кадров, реформы образования, современная педагогика, подход STEAM, искусственный интеллект, конкурентоспособность, устойчивое развитие, духовные ценности.

Ta'lim - bu faqatgina bilim berish jarayoni emas, balki shaxsning ma'naviy, intellektual va madaniy shakllanishida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydigan jarayondir. Jamiyatning taraqqiyoti inson kapitalining sifatiga bevosita bog'liq. Inson kapitali esa, o'z navbatida, sifatli ta'lim orqali shakllanadi [3, 214-b.]. Rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasiga nazar tashlasak, ularda ta'lim tizimiga alohida ustuvorlik berilganini ko'ramiz. Masalan, Yaponiya, Janubiy Koreya yoki Germaniya kabi davlatlar urush yoki inqirozdan keyin ham eng katta sarmoyani ta'limga yo'naltirgan. Natijada, ular qisqa fursatda iqtisodiy jihatdan kuchli, barqaror va yuqori texnologiyali mamlakatlarga aylangan.

Ta'limning strategik vazifasi - yosh avlodni nafaqat bilim bilan qurollantirish, balki ularda Vatanga sadoqat, mas'uliyat, mustaqil fikrlash va mehnatsevarlik kabi sifatlarni shakllantirishdan iborat [4, 92-b.]. Ta'lim va iqtisodiy taraqqiyot o'rtasidagi uzviy bog'liqlik

Ta'lim tizimi kuchli bo'lgan jamiyatda iqtisodiy rivojlanish sur'atlari ham yuqori bo'ladi. Chunki bilimli insonlar mehnat unumdorligini oshiradi, innovatsiyalarni ishlab chiqadi va yangi texnologiyalarni amaliyotga tatbiq etadi. Shuning uchun ta'lim - iqtisodiy o'sishning harakatlantiruvchi kuchi sifatida qaraladi [5, 178-b.].

Misol uchun, Finlyandiya dunyoda ta'lim sifatiga ko'ra ilg'or o'rinlardan birini egallaydi. Bu mamlakatda iqtisodiy resurslar ko'p bo'lmasa-da, yuqori malakali kadrlar tufayli innovatsion iqtisodiyot shakllangan. O'zbekiston ham oxirgi yillarda aynan kadrlar salohiyatini oshirish

orqali raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyot sari odimlamoqda [6, 203-b.]. Ta'limning iqtisodiyotga ta'siri uch asosiy yo'nalishda namoyon bo'ladi:

- Inson kapitali sifatini oshirish - malakali ishchi kuchi shakllanadi.
- Ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini ko'tarish - raqobatbardoshlik ortadi.
- Innovatsion rivojlanishni jadallashtirish - yangi texnologiyalar yaratiladi.

Ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilish - davr talabi

XXI asrda ta'lim tizimi ilgari bo'lgan shakldan tubdan farq qiladi. Axborot texnologiyalari, raqamli platformalar, sun'iy intellekt, masofaviy ta'lim kabi yangiliklar o'quv jarayoniga kirib keldi. Shuning uchun ta'limni zamonaviylashtirish - nafaqat zarurat, balki strategik ehtiyojdir [7, 55-b.].

O'zbekiston Respublikasida so'nggi yillarda ta'lim sohasida ko'plab islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarini kengaytirish, umumiy o'rta ta'lim sifatini oshirish, oliy ta'limga qabul kvotalarini kengaytirish va xorijiy tajribani joriy etish bu boradagi muhim qadamlar bo'ldi. Yangi avlod darsliklari, STEAM yondashuvi, mustaqil ta'lim ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, xalqaro standartlarga mos ta'lim dasturlari - bularning barchasi jamiyat taraqqiyotiga xizmat qiladi [8, 146-b.].

Ta'lim va ijtimoiy barqarorlik: Sifatli ta'lim nafaqat iqtisodiy, balki ijtimoiy barqarorlikning ham kafolatidir. Bilimli va ongli fuqarolar huquqiy jamiyatning shakllanishida faol ishtirok etadi. Ular qonunlarga rioya qiladi, ijtimoiy jarayonlarda befarq bo'lmaydi va jamiyatning rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shadi [9, 72-b.]. Bundan tashqari, ta'lim savodxonlik darajasini oshiradi, jaholat va ekstremistik qarashlarga qarshi eng samarali vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham BMT va UNESCO kabi xalqaro tashkilotlar ta'limni inson huquqlarining asosiy elementi sifatida e'tirof etgan.

Kelajak sari - ta'limga investitsiya: Yosh avlodning bugungi olgan ta'limi - ertangi kunning taraqqiyoti demakdir. Maktab, kollej va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida shakllanayotgan bilim, ko'nikma va qadriyatlar mamlakatning iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy kelajagini belgilaydi. Shu bois, har bir davlatning eng to'g'ri strategiyasi - bu ta'limga sarmoya kiritishdir [10, 190-b.]. Kuchli ta'lim tizimi - kuchli iqtisodiyot, mustahkam ijtimoiy tuzum va barqaror taraqqiyotning kafolati bo'lib qolaveradi.

Ta'lim insonni tarbiyalaydi, tafakkurini kengaytiradi, uning mehnat bozorida raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi va jamiyatga foydali shaxs sifatida shakllantiradi. Shu bois, ta'limga bo'lgan sadoqat va e'tibor - bu aslida kelajakka bo'lgan sadoqatdir.

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O'QUVCHILARNING OG'ZAKI NUTQINI O'STIRISHDA SAVOL-JAVOB DISKURSINING AHAMIYATI

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role and significance of interrogative pronouns in developing students' oral speech skills during the process of teaching English. It highlights the possibilities of using interrogative pronouns (Who, What, Which, When, Why) to foster students' communicative competence, independent thinking, and speech activity. The article demonstrates the semantic and syntactic features of interrogative pronouns, their Uzbek equivalents, and effective methods of applying them in the learning process through practical examples. In particular, it discusses ways to enhance students' logical thinking and reinforce their grammatical and lexical skills through question-and-answer exercises. According to the findings, systematic use of interrogative pronouns serves as an effective means of improving students' oral communication skills.

Keywords: interrogative pronouns, oral speech, communication, question-and-answer exercises, English teaching methodology, grammatical competence, speech activity, learning process.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida so'roq olmoshlarining o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutqini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati tahlil etilgan. So'roq olmoshlari (Who, What, Which, When, Why) yordamida o'quvchilarning muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish, mustaqil fikrlash va nutqiy faoliyatni faollashtirish imkoniyatlari yoritilgan. Maqolada so'roq olmoshlarining semantik-sintaktik xususiyatlari, ularning o'zbek tilidagi ekvivalentlari hamda o'quv jarayonida ulardan samarali foydalanish metodlari amaliy misollar asosida ko'rsatib berilgan. Xususan, savol-javob mashqlari orqali o'quvchilarda mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish, grammatik va leksik ko'nikmalarni mustahkamlash yo'llari bayon etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, so'roq olmoshlaridan tizimli foydalanish o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutqini faollashtirishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'roq olmoshlari, og'zaki nutq, muloqot, savol-javob mashqlari, ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasi, grammatik ko'nikma, nutqiy faoliyat, o'quv jarayoni.

Respublikamizning jahon hamjamiyatida tutgan o'rni tobora o'sib, xalqaro aloqalar, savdo – sotiq, turizm va mamlakatlar orasidagi madaniy hamda iqtisodiy aloqalar rivojlanib, mustahkamlanib borayotgan bir paytda uning kelajagini yaratuvchi yoshlarga ingliz tilini puxta o'rgatish va horijliklar bilan muloqat davomida o'ziga taalluqli masalalarni erkin muhokama qila olish, umuman, og'zaki va yozma shaklda muloqat qila olishni o'rgatish hozirgi kunning eng dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir. [1] Shuningdek, horijiy tillarni o'rganish jamiyatning ijtimoiy iqtisodiy, ilmiy – texnikaviy va umummadaniy taraqqiyotining omili bo'lsa, darslar jarayonida muntazam ravishda o'rgatib borish va aloqa sifatida undan foydalanish ko'pchilik o'quvchilarni fanni sevmaliklarini oldini oladi, o'qitishni jozibador qiladi va o'quvchini chet tilini o'zlashtira olishini ta'minlaydi.

So'roq olmoshlarining semantik sintaktik xususiyatlaridan biri kishi nomlari va boshqa nomlar uchun (hayvonot, parranda va predmetlar) ikki xil ishlatilishidir. Who o'zbek tilida Kim? Olmoshiga to'g'ri keladi va faqat odamlar uchun ishlatiladi. What o'zbek tilidagi Nima? So'roq olmoshiga o'xshash bo'lib, faqat jonsiz predmetlar, hayvonot va parranda boshqa otlarga nisbatan ishlatiladi [2].

Masalan: *Who came? Kim keldi?*
What happened? Nima bo'ldi?

Chet tilini savol – javoblar orqali muvofaqiyatli egallash o'qituvchiga uning ish metodikasiga, foydalanadigan nutqiy vaziyatiga va studentga bog'liqdir. O'qituvchi og'zaki nutqni o'stirish ustida ishlar ekan o'zining ma'lum sistemasiga ega bo'ladi. Ana shunday

sistemaning komponentlaridan biri, talabaning o'quv qo'llanmadagi matnga doir savol – javob mashqlarini tashkil qilishdir. O'z ustida ishlaydigan har bir o'qituvchi o'z guruhidagi talabalarning bilim darajasiga, darsni o'tishda guruh oldiga qo'ygan maqsadiga ko'ra matn ustida ishlashning o'ziga xos yangi usullarini yarata oladi.

Turli xildagi usullarni yaratishda esa so'roq olmoshlari eng muhim tayanch so'z hisoblanib, o'quvchini ijodiy fikrlashga va matn haqida yetarlicha ko'nikmaga ega bo'lishiga undaydi. [5] Quyida darsda o'tilgan "A Freshmen's experience" matni bo'yicha talabalar bajargan mustaqil ish topshiriqlaridan namuna sifatida keltiramiz.

1. Matndan nutq namunasini ko'chirib yozing va shu asosida gap tuzing.

Javob: *"I didn't know that people used to be monkey's, or that George Eliot was a lady"*

2. Yozgan nutq namunangizdan foydalanib matga maxsus savollar tuzing va unga javob qaytaring.

Javob: *Who didn't know that people used to be monkeys, or that George Eliot was a lady?*

What she didn't know?

Whom she didn't know that she was a lady?

Who was Eliot?

Why Judy didn't know that people used to be a monkey? Etc....

Shu kabi misolllar davom etishi mumkin. Yuqorida berilgan savollar gapning turli variantini tuzish uchun xizmat qiladi. Berilgan har bir misoldagi mantiqiy urg'uga qarab gapdagi fikr maqsad o'zgarishi ko'zda tutilgan. O'quvchilarga mantiqiy urg'u berishni ham so'roq olmoshlari yordamida gap tuzish mashqi orqali o'rgitish mumkin.

Og'zaki nutqni o'stirishda so'roq olmoshlarining faollashuvi muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, undan talabani og'zaki nutq faoliyatini o'stirishda qanchalik sistemali tarzda foydalanilsa, o'quvchining fikrlash doirasi va nutqi, lug'at boyligi va grammatik qoidalarni o'zlashtirishi oshib boradi. So'roq olmoshlarining ishlatilishini yaxshi o'zlashtirgan talabalar uchun auditoriyada savol – javoblar o'tkazilishi uchun qulay sharoit yaratilsa o'quv nutqiy vaziyatlar bilan ishlashga o'yin tusi berilsa, talabani chet tilida gaplashishga kirishuvidan "qo'rqishlqri" bartaraf qilinsa, talaba tashabbusi rag'batlantirilsagina nutqiy vaziyatlar bilan ishlashda yaxshi imkoniyatlarga erishish mumkin va shu asosida chet itlini o'qitish metodikasida ham odatda o'quv materialini o'zlashtirish va undan nutqda foydalanish mashqlarini alohida ajratib ko'rsatganlar.

Tor doiradagi til vositalaridan foydalanib o'z fikrlarini bayon qilish va dialogik tarzda nutqni o'stirish mashqlari ancha muvofaqqiyatli sanaladi. Masalan: Talabalar qisqa matnni tinglab bo'lgach, undagi yo'q ma'lumotlarni tiklashga yordam beradigan savollarga javob qaytaradilar ya'ni so'roq olmoshlari orqali bir – birining voqelikka aloqador bo'lgan fikrlarini bilib oladilar. Shu munosabat bilan talabalar mana bunday topshiriq oladilar:

Listen to the text and ask questions for more information.

But now when the girls talk about the things that I never heard of, I just keep still and look them up in the encyclopedia. And anyway, I'm just as bright in class as any of the others, and brighter than some of them!

Talabalar matnni tinglagach, o'zlarini qiziqtirgan lekin matnda tilga olinmagan narsalar haqida so'ray boshlaydilar. Ushbu jarayonda so'roq olmoshlarining aktiv ishtiroki va to'g'ri qo'llanilishi talabaning erkin fikrlay olish doirasini kengaytiruvchi asosiy omil hisoblanadi.

1. *Why she used to read encyclopedia?*

2. *Whom did she talk with?*

3. *What made her to be a bright girl?*

Ish tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, talabalarni mavzu situatsiya yuzasidan bog'langan savollar berishga o'rgatish mashqlarini qo'llash talabani juft bo'lib ishlashlarida va mustaqil ishlarni tashkil qilishda qo'l keladi va sermazmun o'tadi. Talabani chet tilida erkin so'zlay olishi uchun dars turli shakldanutqiy namunalardan valeksik birliklardan foydalanib: dars – teleko'prik, dars – sayohat, dars – anjuman, “Nima? Qachon? Qayerda?” va shu kabi tashkil qilinishi mumkin. Bunday darslar orqali o'quvchilar mavzularni qanday o'rganganliklarini ko'ra oladilar va erishilgan yutuqdan mamnuniyat his qila oladilar.

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THE ROLE OF ACTIVE LISTENING TECHNIQUES IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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Abstract. This paper explores the importance of developing listening skills with a special focus on active listening techniques in educational and professional communication. Active listening goes beyond simply hearing words; it involves concentration, empathy, understanding, and appropriate response to the speaker. The study discusses key techniques such as maintaining eye contact, giving verbal and non-verbal feedback, asking clarifying questions, and avoiding premature judgment. Applying these strategies helps improve communication, build stronger relationships, and enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: listening skills, active listening, communication, empathy, feedback, concentration, attention, non-verbal communication, understanding, collaboration, education, professional growth.

In the field of education and communication studies, listening is often described as one of the most fundamental yet overlooked language skills. While speaking and writing are usually emphasized in academic settings, **listening** plays a vital role in achieving mutual understanding, effective interaction, and learning success. According to **Brownell (2012)**, listening is not a passive process but an active effort that involves interpreting messages, understanding emotions, and responding thoughtfully. **Active listening** differs from passive listening because it requires full mental and emotional engagement with the speaker. It involves focusing attention, interpreting both verbal and non-verbal cues, and providing feedback that shows understanding. In educational contexts, active listening contributes to improved student–teacher relationships, enhances classroom participation, and supports collaborative learning (Wolvin & Coakley, 1996). Moreover, in professional and personal life, active listening promotes empathy, reduces misunderstandings, and strengthens trust. As **Rogers and Farson (1987)** argue, genuine listening helps individuals connect on a deeper level and develop more meaningful communication. This paper aims to examine the concept

of active listening, identify its key techniques, and demonstrate its significance for effective communication in both academic and professional contexts.

Unlocking understanding: mastering active listening: In the modern world of constant digital communication, truly understanding others has become a rare yet invaluable skill. **Active listening** is the process of focusing entirely on the speaker to comprehend not only the content of the message but also its underlying emotions and intentions. According to **Nichols (2009)**, effective listeners engage their minds and emotions simultaneously, seeking to understand the speaker's perspective rather than simply waiting for their turn to speak. Active listening involves **concentration and empathy**. Listeners must eliminate distractions, maintain eye contact, and show genuine interest. Positive body language such as nodding, smiling, and leaning slightly forward signals attentiveness. This creates a comfortable environment where the speaker feels valued.

The power of presence: beyond hearing to understanding: Listening is more than perceiving sounds; it is about being fully present in the communication process. Presence means giving undivided attention-mentally, physically, and emotionally. It involves setting aside distractions and internal judgments to truly focus on what the other person is saying. According to Brown (2010), presence allows listeners to move beyond surface-level comprehension and reach deeper understanding. When listeners show they care about the speaker's message, communication becomes more authentic. In classrooms, this presence helps teachers understand students' needs better and helps students grasp lessons more effectively. In professional settings, presence strengthens teamwork and builds trust among colleagues.

Tools for engagement: practical active listening techniques: Active listening can be developed through practice and self-awareness. The following techniques help improve listening effectiveness: Pay undivided attention: Avoid distractions and demonstrate attentiveness through facial expressions and posture. Reflect and paraphrase: Summarize the speaker's ideas in your own words to confirm understanding (e.g., "So, what I hear you saying is..."). Ask clarifying questions: Encourage deeper discussion with open-ended questions such as "Can you explain more about that?" Avoid premature judgment: Listen with an open mind, withholding opinions until the speaker finishes. Use non-verbal feedback: Nod, maintain eye contact, and use facial expressions that show empathy and understanding. As Imhof (2008) notes, these techniques help listeners process information accurately and respond meaningfully, which enhances interpersonal communication in both educational and organizational settings.

In personal relationships: Listening with empathy deepens emotional bonds and reduces conflicts. People who feel heard are more likely to communicate openly and honestly. By consistently practicing these skills, individuals can transform communication into an effective and empathetic process, strengthening both professional competence and personal growth. Active listening is more than a communication strategy-it is a core life skill essential for building understanding, empathy, and collaboration. By paying attention, asking clarifying questions, and using both verbal and non-verbal feedback, individuals can transform interactions into meaningful exchanges. In education, active listening fosters better learning and classroom communication; in professional settings, it enhances leadership and teamwork. As Rogers and Farson (1987) emphasize, listening with empathy allows people to connect deeply and resolve conflicts constructively. Developing and practicing active listening therefore leads to stronger relationships, improved academic performance, and more effective communication in all areas of life.

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THE ROLE OF VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN EDUCATION AND EVERYDAY LIFE

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Abstract: Communication is one of the most essential aspects of human life. It enables people to share information, express emotions, and build social and professional relationships. This article discusses two major forms of communication-verbal and non-verbal-and analyzes how they complement each other in everyday situations and educational contexts. By exploring their meanings, characteristics, and interdependence, the article highlights the importance of developing both verbal and non-verbal communication skills for successful interaction and effective teaching.

Keywords: communication, verbal communication, non-verbal communication, education, interaction, body language, listening

Communication is the foundation of human society, enabling individuals to exchange ideas, express emotions, and collaborate toward shared goals. From early childhood, humans develop communication skills through sounds, gestures, and words that evolve into complex systems of language and behavior. Without communication, people could not cooperate, share knowledge, or form meaningful relationships. It is present in all aspects of life-families, workplaces, schools, and communities-and is essential for learning, problem-solving, and emotional connection. In education, communication plays a particularly significant role as it shapes the interaction between teachers and students, allowing educators to motivate learners, clarify ideas, and create positive learning environments. There are two primary types of communication: verbal and non-verbal. Verbal communication involves spoken or written words, while non-verbal communication includes gestures, facial expressions, posture, and tone. Although they differ in form, both are interdependent and work together to ensure full understanding. Verbal communication allows people to convey ideas directly and precisely. It includes clarity, grammar, pronunciation, tone, and listening skills. Effective verbal communication is key in classrooms where teachers explain lessons, provide feedback, and ask questions that stimulate critical thinking.

However, even the most well-structured speech may fail if it lacks sensitivity to the listener's context or emotions. Non-verbal communication, in contrast, conveys messages without words through body language, eye contact, touch, and tone of voice. It reveals emotions that words may hide-such as sincerity, discomfort, or enthusiasm. A smile, nod, or

open gesture can reinforce a teacher's message, while crossed arms or a lack of eye contact may signal confusion or disengagement. In many interactions, non-verbal cues are even more powerful than words because they communicate authenticity. For example, when someone says "I'm fine" but appears upset, listeners are more likely to trust their non-verbal signals. In education, non-verbal communication helps teachers maintain classroom control and foster engagement. Gestures and facial expressions make explanations clearer and more dynamic, while students' posture and eye contact reveal their level of interest. Cultural differences also influence non-verbal behavior, highlighting the need for educators to be culturally aware to avoid misunderstandings.

Verbal and non-verbal communication often work together to create meaning. When these two forms are consistent, they reinforce each other—for instance, a teacher saying "Great job!" with a warm smile delivers a stronger, more positive impact. Conversely, when they contradict, confusion arises; listeners usually believe non-verbal cues over words, as Mehrabian (2017) suggests. In classrooms and professional settings, effective use of both forms of communication strengthens cooperation, understanding, and trust. Teachers who combine expressive speech with open gestures and eye contact foster motivation and confidence among students. Communication is the bridge between teachers and learners; through it, knowledge is transmitted and learning occurs. Verbal communication helps deliver lessons and structure classroom discussions, while non-verbal communication maintains engagement and expresses enthusiasm. When both teachers and students communicate clearly and respectfully, learning becomes more active and collaborative. Ultimately, communication—both verbal and non-verbal—is the cornerstone of human connection. It not only enables learning but also nurtures empathy, leadership, and mutual respect. By mastering both forms, individuals become more effective communicators who can build trust, resolve conflicts, and succeed academically, professionally, and personally.

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION O'QITISH METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlanishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan pedagogik jarayon murakkab, shu bilan birga rang-barangdir. Ta'lim-tarbiya samaradorligiga erishishda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlaridagi har bir faoliyat turini to'g'ri tashkil qilish lozim. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish, va ularning samaradorligi haqida bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti, zamonaviy yondashuv, innovatsiya, tarbiyalanuvchi hamda tarbiyachi, bolalar psixologiyasi, rivojlanish, ta'lim, tarbiya, innovatsion texnologiyalar.

“Agar mendan sizni nima qiynaydi?” deb so‘rasangiz, farzandlarimning ta‘lim va tarbiyasi deb javob beraman.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

Maktabgacha ta‘lim mutaxassislari ta‘lim tizimida innovatsion g‘oyalarni yaratish va joriy etish zamonaviy bolalar bog‘chasini rivojlantirish uchun zaruriy shartdir degan fikrga kelishib olishadi. Moliyalashtirish yuzasidan davlat muassasalari “Maktabgacha tarbiyachiga pul ketayotganda” innovatsion tashkiliy yechimlarining kundalik tartibida kiradigan innovatsion tashkiliy yechimlarning kunlik tartibiga kiritilishi institutning obro‘cini sezilarli darajada oshiradi va rivojlanishning keyingi yo‘nalishlarini belgilab beradi. O‘quv jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish Psixofizik yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda, maktabgacha tarbiyachilar tomonidan har doim ijobiy seziladi, ular faoliyatni osongina o‘zgartiradilar.

Maktabgacha yoshi - bu bolaning atrofida dunyoni faol o‘rganadigan davr. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar o‘zlarining psixologik rivojlanish xususiyatlariga ega. Yurish boshlaganida, bola juda ko‘p kashfiyotlar qiladi, xonada, ko‘chada, bolalar bog‘chasida joylashgan narsalar bilan tanishadi. Turli narsalarni yig‘ish, ularni o‘rganish, mavzudan kelib chiqqan tovushlarni tinglash, bu ob‘ektning qaysi fazilatlarini va xususiyatlarini borligini biladi. Ushbu davrda bolaning ingl. -figurativ va ingl. Effektiv fikrlash shakllari yaratilgan. 5-6 yoshligida bola shimgich kabi barcha ma‘lumotlarni so‘radi. Olimlar ushbu yoshlik davrida bolaning bu ma‘lumotni esga olishini, bundan keyin u hayotda hech qachon eslamasligini isbotladi. Bola ufqlarini kengaytiradi oladigan har qanday narsaga qiziqish uyg‘otadigan davrdir va bu uning atrofida dunyoni qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi. XXI asr texnika va texnologiyalar asri. Bu zamonda yangiliksiz, izlanishsiz, yaratuvchanliksiz inson mustaqil individ sifatida hayotda o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lolmaydi. XXI asr texnika va texnologiyalar asri hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda har bir oilada texnik qurilmalar – masalan, mobil telefonlari, televizor, kompyuter, planshet va boshqalar kundalik iste‘molda keng qo‘llanadi. Shunisi diqqatga sazovorki, kichik yoshdagi bolalar kattalarga nisbatan bu qurilmalardan tez va oson foydalanishadi. Ammo, maqsadga yo‘naltirilganlik darajasi juda oddiy. Shu ma‘noda, maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlarini to‘liq texnologiyalar bilan ta‘minlanish bosqichiga o‘tilmoqda. Bu esa ta‘limda ko‘rgazmali qurollardan, zamonaviy texnologiyalar asosida foydalanish imkoniyatini kengaytiradi.

Xususan, yurtboshimiz Sh.Mirziyoyev maktabgacha ta‘lim tizimi haqida quyidagi fikrlarni bejizga bildirmagan edilar: “Aslida, farzandlarimiz tarbiyasida eng asosiy bo‘g‘in hisoblangan maktabgacha ta‘lim tizimining jamiyatimiz hayotidagi o‘rni va ahamiyatini hech narsa bilan o‘lchab bo‘lmaydi. Aynan maktabgacha ta‘lim sohasiga bo‘lgan e‘tibor mamlakatning ertangi taraqqiyoti uchun mustahkam zamin yaratadi”[1]. Maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlarida tashkil etilayotgan mashg‘ulotlarda qo‘llanilayotgan interfaol usullar ta‘lim samaradorligi hamda muhitini yaxshilaydi. Ta‘lim innovatsiyasi deyilganda avvalo mashg‘ulotlarda pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish nazarda tutiladi. Tarbiyachining kasbiy mahorati oshadi. Bolalar ijtimoiy muhitda, jamoasida o‘z o‘rnini his qila boshlaydi. Hozirgi kun talabi tez o‘zgaruvchan, murakkab va o‘zaro bir-biriga bog‘liq dunyoda o‘z o‘rnini topa oladigan shaxsni tarbiyalashdir.

Kreativlik (lot ing. “sreate”–yaratish, “sreative” yaratuvchi ijodkor)–individning yangi g‘oyalarni ishlab chiqarishga tayyorlikni tavsiflovchi hamda mustaqil omil sifatida iqtidorlikning tarkibiga kiruvchi ijodiy qobiliyati ma‘nosini ifodalaydi Shaxsning kreativligi uning tafakkurida, muloqotida, his-tuyg‘ularida, muayyan faoliyat turlarida namoyon bo‘ladi. Kreativlik shaxsni yaxlit holda yoki uning muayyan xususiyatlarini, zehni o‘tkirlikni

tavsiflaydi. Shuningdek, kreativlik iqtidorning muhim omili sifatida aks etadi. Mutaxassislarining ta'kidlashicha, shtatlardagi innovatsion texnologiyalar nafaqat mumkin, balki ehtiyoj ham. Biroq, buni yodda tutish kerak pedagogik texnologiyalar maktabgacha bolalarning o'quv jarayonida qo'llanilishi mumkin, bir nechta qat'iy talablar berildi. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi:

Umuman olganda, maktabgacha yoshdagi yoshlar xotirjamlik hissi bilan ajralib turadi. Ularning kichik sabablarga ko'ra ziddiyatlari va kuchli affektiv epizootiyalari yo'q. Biroq, bu bolaning hissiy hayotining to'yinganligi pasayadi degani emas. Axir, preschooler kuni juda ko'p his-tuyg'ularga to'lib ketadi, shuning uchun kechqurun bola charchagan va to'liq charchash uchun keladi. Bu davrda hissiy jarayonlarning tuzilishi ham o'zgaradi. Ilgari motorli va vegetativ reaksiyalar maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda saqlanib qolgan emotsional jarayonlarga kiritilgan, ammo hissiyotlarning tashqi ifodasi yanada cheklangan shaklga ega bo'ladi. Maktab o'quvchilari nafaqat bugungi kunda qilayotgan ishidan, balki kelajakda nima qilishidan ham xafa bo'lib, xursand bo'lishadi. Presedrga tegishli bo'lgan har bir narsa - rasm, o'yin, qolib tuzish, onaga yordam berish, uy ishlarini bajarish - yorqin hissiy rangga ega bo'lishi kerak, aks holda narsalar tezda yiqilay yoki umuman bo'lmaydi. Chunki bu yoshdagi bola unga qiziq bo'lmagan ishni bajarolmaydi. Bu asrda, maktabgacha tarbiyachilarning boshqalarga va o'zlariga bo'lgan munosabati muhim ko'rsatkichdir. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar ko'pincha kamchiliklarini tanqid qilishadi, tengdoshlariga shaxsiy xususiyatlar beriladi, bolalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar, shuningdek, kattalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi munosabatni qayd qiladi. Biroq, ota-onalar bolalarga misol bo'la oladi. Shuning uchun, ota-onalar bolaga ijobiy ma'lumotni kiritish, shaxsiy yoki intellektual ma'lumot bo'lsin, u bolaga qo'rquv, xavotir va haqoratni keltirmasliklari kerak.

Shuningdek, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalar uchun alohida ingliz va rus tili xonalarini tashkil etish foydadan xoli emas. U yerda guruhlar navbat bilan mashg'ulot o'tkazishadi. Bolalar barcha innovatsion texnologiya vositalari, o'yinchoqlar, ko'rgazmalar vositasida mashg'ulot olib borsalar, jihozlarga ham shikast yetmaydi, nurlanishning oldi ham olinadi. Muhimi, bunday alohida xonalar bo'ylab yurish bolalarga yaxshi ta'sir qiladi. Ularda ana shunday xonalarga bo'lgan intilish darsga bo'lgan qiziqishning ortib borishiga sabab bo'ladi. Xonaga kirganda bolalar o'zlarini xuddi chet elga tushib qolgandek his qilishlari uchun xona devorlari ham aynan shunday beztiladi. O'yinchoqlar berilganda tarbiyachi har bir o'yinchoqning inglizcha nomini aytib asta sekinlik bilan bolalarga o'rgatishi kerak.

Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar jamiyat va mamalakat taraqqiyoti bilan jadal suratda rivojlanib boradi. Shunday ekan, endilikda juda katta doimiy ish o'rinlariga ega tsex hamda fabrikalar yonida kelajakda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlariga ehtiyoj paydo bo'ladi. Bunda uzoqroqda yashaydigan tarbiyalanuvchilarni olib keluvchi alohida avtobuslar tashkil qilish, bunday muassasalarning ish tartibi va dasturlari haqida fikr yuritish ham alohida muammolardan hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy, innovatsion o'qitish usullarini qo'llash. Bunday usullar bolajak mutaxassisning kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishga, o'quvchilarni faol bilim va amaliy faoliyatga jalb etishga, bilish jarayonida tashabbuskorlikni namoyon etishga yo'naltirilgan bo'lishi kerak. Ta'lim dasturlarini passiv assimilyatsiya qilish istisno qilinadi.

Ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy infratuzilmaning mavjudligi. U o'qitishning yangi shakl va usullarini, xususan, masofaviy ta'limni qo'llashga yordam beradigan axborot, texnologik, tashkiliy va kommunikatsiya komponentlariga asoslanishi kerak. Ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalar o'qitishda muayyan yondashuvlarni qo'llash asosida qo'llaniladi, ya'ni yangi texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish uchun asos bo'lgan talablar va maqsadlarni o'z ichiga olgan tamoyillar. Pedagogik sohadagi barcha innovatsiyalar jamiyat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishining hozirgi bosqichiga qat'iy mos kelishiga asoslanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda ular

o'quvchilarning mustaqilligini rivojlantirishga, o'z-o'zini o'rganish va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirishga, o'quv dasturlarini mexanik ravishda emas, balki ongli ravishda o'zlashtirishga qaratilishi kerak. Mamlakatimizdagi deyarli barcha maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari zamonaviy kompyuter va telekommunikatsiya texnologiyalari bilan jihozlangan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, tarbiyachilarning o'z mehnat faoliyatlariga yangicha yondashuvlarini talab etadi. Ta'lim jarayoniga yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etilishi, tarbiyachini texnik vositalar tomonidan siqib chiqishiga emas, balki yangicha yondashuv orqali uning vazifasi va rolini o'zgartirib, tarbiyachilik faoliyatini yana-da serqirra, ijodiy va kreativ yondashuvga asoslangan kasbga aylantiradi.

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O'QITUVCHINING BOLA PSIXOLOGIYASINI TUSHUNISHDAGI ROLI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'qituvchining ta'lim jarayonida bola psixologiyasini chuqur tushunishining ahamiyati yoritiladi. Bola psixologiyasi pedagogning muloqot madaniyati, motivatsion yondashuvi va tarbiyaviy faoliyati samaradorligiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Maqolada o'qituvchining emotsional muhit yaratish, individual yondashuvni amalga oshirish, ijobiy motivatsiya berish hamda konfliktlarni boshqarishdagi roli tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: bola psixologiyasi, o'qituvchi, ta'lim jarayoni, emotsional muhit, motivatsiya.

Annotation: This article highlights the importance of a teacher's deep understanding of child psychology in the educational process. Child psychology directly influences the teacher's communication culture, motivational approach, and the effectiveness of educational activities. The article analyzes the teacher's role in creating an emotional environment, applying an individual approach, providing positive motivation, and managing conflicts.

Keywords: child psychology, teacher, educational process, emotional environment, motivation.

Аннотация: В статье раскрывается значение глубокого понимания учителем детской психологии в образовательном процессе. Детская психология напрямую влияет на коммуникативную культуру педагога, его мотивационный подход и эффективность воспитательной деятельности. В статье анализируется роль учителя в создании эмоциональной среды, реализации индивидуального подхода, формировании позитивной мотивации и управлении конфликтами.

Ключевые слова: детская психология, учитель, образовательный процесс, эмоциональная среда, мотивация.

Har bir jamiyatning taraqqiyoti, eng avvalo, uning ta'lim tizimi va o'qituvchilarining malakasi bilan belgilanadi. O'qituvchi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki shaxs tarbiyalovchi, jamiyat kelajagini shakllantiruvchi muhim shaxsdir. Shu sababli zamonaviy o'qituvchidan o'z fanini mukammal bilish bilan birga, bola psixologiyasini ham chuqur tushunish talab etiladi. Bola psixologiyasini anglamagan pedagog o'quvchi bilan to'g'ri muloqot o'rnatmaydi, bu esa ta'lim samaradorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosiy tamoyilga aylangan. Har bir o'quvchining individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish, uning hissiy holatini e'tiborga olish o'qituvchining psixologik savodxonligiga bog'liqdir. Agar o'qituvchi bolaning ruhiy kechinmalarini anglay olsa, u o'quvchini to'g'ri yo'naltira oladi, uning qiziqishlarini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va salbiy holatlarning oldini oladi.

Bola psixologiyasi bu bolaning yoshiga xos ruhiy, hissiy, aqliy va ijtimoiy rivojlanish jarayonlarini o'rganuvchi fan bo'lib, u pedagogik faoliyatda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bola dunyoni o'ziga xos tarzda idrok etadi, shuning uchun unga to'g'ri ta'sir ko'rsatish uchun o'qituvchi uning psixologik xususiyatlarini chuqur bilishi zarur. Har bir yosh davrining o'ziga xos psixologik ehtiyojlari mavjud. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar o'yin orqali o'rganadi, kichik maktab yoshi davrida esa e'tirof va baho bolaning asosiy rag'bat manbaiga aylanadi. Shu bois o'qituvchi dars jarayonini o'quvchilarning yosh xususiyatlariga mos tarzda tashkil etishi, ularning diqqatini to'g'ri yo'naltira olishi lozim.

O'qituvchi bola psixologiyasini chuqur bilganida, u dars jarayonida ijobiy emotsional muhit yaratishga, o'quvchilarning shaxsiy farqlarini inobatga olishga va ularga individual yondashuvni qo'llashga intiladi. Darsda iliq, do'stona muhit hukm sursa, o'quvchilar o'z fikrlarini erkin ifoda etadi, xatolardan qo'rqmaydi va o'z ustida ishlashga intiladi. Ijobiy motivatsiya o'quvchi shaxsining rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. Maqto'v, rag'bat va e'tirof bolaning o'ziga ishonchini oshiradi, o'qishga qiziqishini kuchaytiradi. Aksincha, kamsitish yoki tanbeh bolaning ruhiyatiga salbiy ta'sir qiladi va o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini susaytiradi.

O'qituvchi sinf jamoasidagi nizolarni bartaraf etishda ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bola psixologiyasini yaxshi bilgan pedagog bunday vaziyatlarda yumshoqlik bilan, tarbiyaviy yondashuv asosida harakat qiladi. Bunday yondashuv bolalarda muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantiradi va sinfda sog'lom psixologik muhitni ta'minlaydi. Bola o'qituvchini nafaqat bilim manbai, balki mehribon murabbiy sifatida qabul qilganida, u o'zini himoyalangan, qadrlangan inson sifatida his etadi.

Bola psixologiyasini tushunish, shuningdek, o'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlariga ham bevosita bog'liqdir. Samimiylik, sabr-toqat, empatiya va mehribonlik bu fazilatlar o'qituvchining kasbiy mahoratini to'ldiruvchi, o'quvchilar ishonchini mustahkamlovchi xususiyatlaridir. Psixologlarning ta'kidlashicha, bola o'zining dastlabki muvaffaqiyatlarini aynan o'qituvchining e'tibori va ishonchi tufayli his etadi. Pedagogning har bir so'zi va har bir harakati bolada uzoq muddatli ruhiy iz qoldiradi. Agar bola o'qituvchining samimiyatini sezsa, u bilan muloqotdan zavq oladi, o'qishga qiziqadi va o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etadi.

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarning psixologik tayyorgarligini oshirish masalasi nihoyatda dolzarbdir. Ta'lim muassasalarida o'tkazilayotgan treninglar, seminarlar va psixologik mashg'ulotlar pedagoglarga bolalar bilan samarali muloqot o'rnatish, ularning hissiy ehtiyojlarini anglash va psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash imkonini beradi. Bunday tayyorgarlik o'quvchilarning o'zini anglashi, o'ziga ishonchi va ijtimoiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Natijada ta'lim sifati oshadi, dars jarayoni yanada samarali kechadi va o'quvchilar uchun sog'lom psixologik muhit yaratiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o'qituvchining bola psixologiyasini tushunishdagi roli beqiyosdir. Pedagog nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki bola qalbiga yo'l topuvchi insondir. Bola psixologiyasini chuqur anglagan o'qituvchi o'quv jarayonini samarali tashkil etadi, o'quvchilarda o'ziga ishonch, ijobiy fikrlash va o'qishga muhabbatni shakllantiradi. Bola psixologiyasini o'rganish va uni amaliyotda qo'llash zamonaviy pedagogning eng muhim kasbiy fazilatlaridan biridir. Bunday yondashuv o'quvchilarning ruhiy sog'lomligi va ma'naviy kamolotini ta'minlaydi. Shunday o'qituvchilar tufayli jamiyatda bilimli, mehribon, ruhiy jihatdan barqaror va barkamol avlod voyaga yetadi. Bu esa har qanday mamlakatning eng katta boyligi sanaladi.

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CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS IN MODERN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article explores the current challenges and innovative solutions in modern language education in the 21st century. The authors analyze how technological progress, globalization, and digital transformation have reshaped the ways languages are taught and learned. The study highlights issues such as low student motivation, lack of qualified teachers, digital inequality, and limited professional development opportunities. Furthermore, it introduces innovative teaching approaches such as blended learning, mobile-assisted language learning (MALL), gamification, and artificial intelligence integration. The paper concludes that modern language education must balance traditional pedagogy with technology-driven innovation to develop communicative competence, intercultural understanding, and lifelong learning habits.

Keywords: language education, innovation, digital learning, communicative competence, pedagogy, artificial intelligence, blended learning, motivation, digital literacy, modern teaching.

Introduction: Education in the 21st century is experiencing rapid transformation. The advancement of information technology and globalization has changed the way students access and process knowledge. Language education, as one of the most vital aspects of human communication, faces new opportunities and challenges in adapting to these global shifts. The need for multilingual competence, digital literacy, and intercultural awareness has become central to modern pedagogy.

In Uzbekistan, this trend aligns with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5847 “On the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.” This decree emphasizes the modernization of education, the digitalization of academic processes, and the integration of innovative teaching methods. Therefore, addressing the current challenges and identifying effective solutions in language education are essential for improving both national and global competitiveness.

Challenges in Modern Language Education: One of the most pressing challenges in language education is the lack of motivation among students. Traditional teaching methods - often limited to grammar-translation and repetition - fail to inspire interest or creativity. Learners frequently study languages as academic requirements rather than as real-life communication tools. As Richards (2020) notes, such methods focus more on accuracy than on fluency, which limits communicative development.

Another major issue is digital inequality. Many educational institutions lack access to modern technologies, creating a gap between privileged and underprivileged learners. Without equal access to the internet, computers, and software, students cannot fully benefit from online resources or virtual collaboration tools. This inequality is especially visible in rural or developing areas.

Teacher preparedness is also a challenge. As Kukulska-Hulme (2022) highlights, digital transformation requires teachers not only to master new technologies but also to redesign their pedagogy. Inadequate professional development opportunities often prevent teachers from integrating innovative tools effectively into their lessons.

Finally, linguistic and cultural diversity adds complexity to classroom instruction. Modern language educators must address varying learner backgrounds, expectations, and levels while fostering intercultural competence and respect for linguistic diversity.

Innovative Pedagogical Solutions: To address these challenges, educators are increasingly adopting innovative, learner-centered approaches. The most influential is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which focuses on meaningful interaction and real-world communication rather than memorization. This approach develops fluency, confidence, and sociolinguistic awareness.

Another significant advancement is Technology-Enhanced Language Learning (TELL). Platforms such as YouTube, Duolingo, and Google Classroom provide students with flexible, interactive, and authentic materials. Teachers, instead of being information transmitters, now act as facilitators who guide students in discovering knowledge independently (Reinders & Benson, 2022).

Blended learning - a combination of online and traditional classroom instruction - offers both flexibility and structure. It allows learners to study at their own pace while maintaining direct teacher support. Research shows that blended learning improves learner autonomy, motivation, and retention (Kukulska-Hulme & Lee, 2023).

Furthermore, mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) uses smartphones and tablets to create dynamic, mobile environments for language practice. Applications such as Memrise and Babbel combine gamification with practical exercises, making learning more engaging and enjoyable (Dooly & O’Dowd, 2021).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming education on a global scale. AI-powered tools can assess student performance, provide instant feedback, and personalize learning materials. For example, intelligent chatbots simulate conversation practice and pronunciation correction. Machine translation tools such as Google Translate and DeepL, while not perfect, help learners analyze linguistic structures in real time.

AI also assists teachers in evaluating assignments, managing class data, and identifying students’ strengths and weaknesses. According to Miller (2022), AI technologies can create inclusive classrooms by supporting students with different learning needs. However, educators must balance automation with the human touch - empathy, encouragement, and creativity remain essential in teaching.

Global Perspectives and Intercultural Communication: Language education today cannot be separated from global communication. The ability to understand cultural nuances is as important as mastering grammar or vocabulary. As Byram (2021) explains, intercultural communicative competence (ICC) enables individuals to interact successfully across cultures. Innovative pedagogy integrates cultural content, online exchange programs, and collaborative projects with international students.

Digital communication platforms also open opportunities for cultural exchange. Video conferences, online debates, and collaborative writing projects connect learners from different countries, enhancing global awareness and respect for diversity.

Conclusion: Modern language education is at a crossroads between traditional teaching values and digital innovation. Teachers must continuously adapt to new tools, rethink classroom strategies, and inspire creativity in students. The key to successful language learning lies in combining effective pedagogical principles with technological advancements. For Uzbekistan and the global academic community, promoting digital literacy, teacher training, and intercultural competence is crucial for shaping the future of education.

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**MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM MUASSASALARIDA RUS TILI DARSLARINI O‘YIN
ORQALI O‘RGATISHNING PEDAGOGIK AHAMIYATI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida rus tilini o'yin texnologiyalari asosida o'rgatishning pedagogik va psixologik ahamiyati, o'yin metodikasining ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni, maqsad va vazifalari, shuningdek, o'yin asosida o'qitishning samarali usullari keng yoritilgan. O'yin faoliyatining bola shaxsini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni, nutq va tafakkur jarayonlariga ta'siri, hamda o'yinli mashg'ulotlarning amaliy ahamiyati haqida ilmiy tahlil keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim, rus tili, o'yin metodikasi, kommunikativ yondashuv, pedagogik innovatsiya.

Annotation: This article highlights the pedagogical and psychological significance of teaching the Russian language in preschool institutions through game-based technologies. It discusses the role, goals, and objectives of game methodology in the educational process, as well as effective methods of teaching through play. The article provides a scientific analysis of the role of play activities in the development of a child's personality, their influence on speech and thinking processes, and the practical importance of game-based lessons.

Key words: preschool education, Russian language, game methodology, communicative approach, pedagogical innovation.

Аннотация: В статье раскрывается педагогическое и психологическое значение обучения русскому языку в дошкольных учреждениях на основе игровых технологий. Рассматриваются роль, цели и задачи игровой методики в образовательном процессе, а также эффективные способы обучения через игру. Приводится научный анализ роли игровой деятельности в развитии личности ребёнка, её влияния на процессы речи и мышления, а также практической значимости игровых занятий.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, русский язык, игровая методика, коммуникативный подход, педагогическая инновация.

Maktabgacha yosh bu inson hayotidagi eng muhim davrlardan biri bo'lib, aynan shu davrda bolaning nutqi, tafakkuri, diqqat va eslab qolish qobiliyati faol rivojlanadi. Shu sababli, bu bosqichda xorijiy tillarni, jumladan rus tilini o'rgatish alohida e'tibor talab etadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining ta'lim sohasiga oid qaror va farmonlarida ham chet tillarni erta yoshdan o'qitish bo'yicha qator vazifalar belgilab berilgan. Rus tilini o'yin orqali o'rgatish metodikasi esa bolalarning tabiiy ehtiyojlariga mos bo'lib, ularda o'rganishga nisbatan ijobiy motivatsiya hosil qiladi. Chunki o'yin bolaning asosiy faoliyat turi sifatida uning bilish jarayonini faollashtiradi, muloqot qilish ehtiyojini oshiradi va o'rganishni qiziqarli jarayonga aylantiradi.

O'yin orqali ta'lim berish bu bolalarning yosh psixologik xususiyatlariga mos holda bilim berishning eng samarali usullaridan biridir. O'yin faoliyati orqali bola yangi so'zlarni eslab qoladi, ularni nutqida qo'llashni o'rganadi, muloqot qilishni mashq qiladi va o'z fikrini ifodalashga intiladi. O'yinli yondashuv rus tili darslarida nafaqat bilim beradi, balki bolaning shaxsiy rivojlanishini ham ta'minlaydi.

O'yinli metodika dars jarayonida bir nechta vazifalarni bajaradi: bolalarda rus tiliga qiziqishni shakllantiradi, eshitish va talaffuz ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi, so'z boyligini kengaytiradi, grammatik qoidalarni tabiiy ravishda o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Eng muhimi, o'yinli darslarda bola faol ishtirokchi bo'ladi.

Quyida rus tilini o'yin orqali o'rgatishda qo'llaniladigan samarali o'yin turlariga misollar keltirilgan:

1. Leksik o'yinlar yangi so'zlarni o'rganish va mustahkamlash uchun qo'llaniladi. Masalan: "Что это?", "Найди картинку", "Цепочка слов" o'yinlari bolalarning so'z boyligini kengaytiradi.

2. Grammatik o'yinlar gap tuzish va so'z shakllarini to'g'ri qo'llashni o'rgatadi. Masalan: "Кто что делаем?", "Подбери слово", "Скажи правильно" kabi o'yinlar grammatik bilimlarni mustahkamlaydi.

3. Rolli o'yinlar bolalarda real hayotiy vaziyatlarda muloqot qilish ko'nikmasini shakllantiradi. Masalan: "В магазине", "В детском саду", "В транспорте" kabi o'yinlar orqali muloqot madaniyati rivojlanadi.

4. Musiqali va harakatli o'yinlar bolalarda ijobiy emotsional muhit yaratadi, so'zlarni ritmik tarzda eslab qolishga yordam beradi.

Pedagogik tajribalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'yin asosida tashkil etilgan mashg'ulotlarda bolalar yangi so'zlarni 23 baravar tezroq o'zlashtiradi. O'yin jarayonida ularning nutq faolligi ortadi, diqqat, xotira va tasavvur rivojlanadi. O'yinli darslar bolaning shaxsiy faolligini oshiradi, ularni o'qishga bo'lgan ichki ehtiyojni kuchaytiradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida rus tili darslarini o'yin orqali o'rgatish bolaning til o'rganish jarayonini tabiiy, zavqli va samarali qiladi. O'yinli mashg'ulotlar bolalarning fikrlash, eslab qolish, muloqot va ijodkorlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi. O'yin asosidagi ta'lim bolaning mustaqil fikrlashini, tilga bo'lgan ishonchini va o'rganishga bo'lgan ijobiy munosabatini shakllantiradi. Shu bois, o'yin texnologiyalari maktabgacha ta'limda rus tilini o'qitishning ajralmas qismi sifatida qaralishi lozim.

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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DESIGNING THINKING METHODS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ORAL SPEECH

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Annotation: This article explores the theoretical foundations underpinning the use of design thinking methods in developing students' oral speech competence. It first reviews classical and contemporary theories of creative thinking, human-centered design, and communicative competence, then examines how design thinking phases (empathize, define, ideate, prototype, test) can be applied in oral speech pedagogy. The study argues that integrating design thinking fosters learner autonomy, iterative refinement of speech, and deeper engagement. Finally, practical implications and directions for future research are suggested.

Keywords: design thinking, oral speech, communicative competence, learner autonomy, iterative pedagogy, creative thinking, human-centered design.

Oral speech competency is a primary aim in language education, and it includes not just grammatical accuracy but also communication efficiency, spontaneity, and flexibility. Traditional techniques frequently emphasise drills, repetition, and teacher-led correction,

which may restrict learners' inventiveness and response. In contrast, design thinking—a human-centered, iterative, and solution-oriented approach—provides a potential theoretical lens for reconsidering how we teach and scaffold oral speech development (von Thienen et al., 2018; Guaman-Quintanilla, 2025).

This research attempts to define the fundamental basis of design thinking methodologies and investigate their use in improving the oral communication abilities of learners. It specifically addresses the following questions.

1. Which theoretical traditions influence design thinking as a methodology?
2. How might design thinking stages be used to oral speech pedagogy?
3. What advantages and disadvantages result from applying design thinking to improve verbal competence?

Theoretical foundations of design thinking include creative thinking and early influences.

Design thinking originated in imaginative problem-solving conventional wisdom. In the 1950s, John E. Arnold's Creative Engineering seminars established the idea that creativity could be taught (von Thienen et al., 2018, p. 14). [Arnold, 1959]. Arnold proposed that creative thinking included reframing challenges, investigating numerous viewpoints, and accepting uncertainty (von Thienen et al., 2018, p. 15).

Following Arnold, Robert H. McKim proposed a need-based design theory that prioritised human needs and value creation (von Thienen et al., 2018, p. 20) [McKim, 1959]. According to McKim, design is ultimately information regarding meeting human wants in context, and designers should iteratively enhance their offerings while paying great attention to consumers' actual interactions with them.

Human-Centered Design and Empathy. Human-centeredness, or sympathy, is a basic element of design thinking that involves intimately understanding the user's or community member's point of view (Plattner et al., quoted in Guaman-Quintanilla, 2025). This theoretical perspective is consistent with constructivist and humanistic pedagogies, which place an emphasis on individual student agency, previous interactions, and comprehension co-construction.

In the context of education, Guaman-Quintanilla contends that design thinking may be defined as a constructivist learning paradigm in which students actively produce, test, and revise their own artefacts (Guaman-Quintanilla, 2025, p.

4. This reflects both Dewey's experiential learning and Piaget's active knowledge production.

Communicative Competence and Oral Speech Theory. To place the importance of design thinking in spoken language pedagogy, someone must first investigate competence in communication theories (Hymes, 1972) and speech act theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969). According to Hymes, successful speech necessitates not just formal grammar skill but also sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competence.

Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory provides additional insight: oral speech develops through social contact and the zone of proximal development, mediated by more proficient interlocutors (Vygotsky, 1978).

Thus, incorporating design thinking must be sensitive to students' zones of possibility of growth and provide built up assistance.

Furthermore, Qurbonova (2023) in *Theoretical Foundations of the Development of Oral Speech Skills* notes that speech training typically combines linguistic, communicative, and methodological components, and emphasises that learners might have difficulty with "language clichés" or deeply embedded errors (p. 19). [Qurbonova; 2023].

3. Design Thinking and Oral Speech Pedagogy:

a) Empathise with the learner's needs. During this phase, teachers and students collaborate to identify the learners' speaking issues, goals, and audience expectations. Interviews, questionnaires, and learner reflections are useful techniques for identifying pain sites (Dikgomo & Ackerdien, 2025, p. 3). For example, a student may suffer with hesitancy or lack of coordination in talks, which becomes a design "problem" to solve.

b) Define/articulate the challenge. After accumulating empathetic facts, learners create an unambiguous problem statement, such as "How can I deliver a persuasive 5-minute speech fluently and with enthusiasm?" This parallels the "How Might We" frame in design thinking (von Thienen et al., 2018, p. 22) [McKim, 1959]. Defining the challenge helps concentrate following ideas.

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EFFECTIVE TEACHING PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: This article discusses the main principles of effective teaching and the integration of innovative methods into modern education. It examines the challenges that teachers face in adapting to rapid technological and pedagogical changes and proposes practical solutions for improving the quality of education. The study also highlights the future prospects of educational innovations and the continuous professional growth of teachers.

Keywords: effective teaching, modern education, learner-centered approach, digital transformation, active learning, blended learning, educational innovation, gamification.

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, education has become a crucial factor in the development of human potential. The traditional model of teaching, based primarily on memorization and passive learning, is no longer sufficient to meet the demands of the 21st century. Today, teachers are expected to be facilitators of learning who encourage independent thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills among students. Modern education emphasizes learner-centered approaches and the use of innovative teaching tools to make learning more engaging, interactive, and relevant.

Effective teaching is based on several fundamental pedagogical principles that ensure both academic success and personal growth of students: 1. Learner-Centered Education – The learning process should focus on students' individual needs, interests, and learning abilities. 2. Active Learning Methods – Discussions, problem-solving tasks, and group work foster deeper understanding and critical thinking. 3. Constructivist Approach – Students build

knowledge through personal experience and reflection, while the teacher serves as a guide and mentor. 4. Continuous Assessment – Regular feedback helps identify learning gaps and supports academic improvement. 5. Integration of Technology – Using digital tools, virtual classrooms, and multimedia resources enhances accessibility and student motivation.

Despite progress in educational reforms, several challenges remain unsolved: - Dominance of Traditional Methods: Many institutions still rely on teacher-centered instruction and rote learning. - Digital Divide: Unequal access to technology limits learning opportunities for students from rural or low-income backgrounds.- Teacher Competency: Not all educators are adequately trained to use modern teaching technologies and innovative pedagogical methods. - Outdated Curricula: Some subjects do not reflect current global and labor market needs. - Low Student Motivation: When lessons lack real-world relevance, students' engagement and curiosity decrease.

To overcome these challenges, educational institutions must implement modern strategies and innovations, including: 1. Blended Learning Models – Combining online and offline instruction allows for flexibility and personalized learning experiences. 2. Project-Based Learning – Students work on real-life projects, which enhances critical thinking and teamwork skills. 3. Gamification and Interactive Platforms – The use of game elements and educational technologies increases motivation and participation. 4. Teacher Professional Development – Regular training in digital pedagogy and soft skills ensures teachers remain effective and adaptable. 5. Inclusive Education Policies – Promoting equal opportunities for all learners, including those with special needs, is essential for fairness and sustainability.

The future of education is closely linked with innovation and technology. Artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and adaptive learning systems are expected to play a significant role in shaping new learning environments. However, the human aspect of education must remain central. Emotional intelligence, ethical values, and collaboration will continue to define the true purpose of learning. The teacher of the future will act as a mentor who guides students toward self-development and lifelong learning.

Effective teaching in modern education is achieved through a combination of traditional pedagogical values and innovative approaches. Teachers must continually improve their professional skills and embrace technological advancements to create an engaging and effective learning environment. Educational innovation is not merely a trend - it is a necessity for preparing students to face the challenges of a rapidly changing world. By following the principles of effective teaching and adopting innovative solutions, the education system can contribute to sustainable social and intellectual progress.

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MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA OILAVIY HAMKORLIKNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlikning ahamiyati va uning bolaning rivojlanishidagi roli yoritilgan. Maqolada ota-ona va tarbiyachi o'rtasidagi samarali muloqot, oilaviy faoliyatni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish, uyda qo'llaniladigan metodlar, oilaning pedagogik jarayonga jalb etilishi hamda bolaning nutq, ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishiga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy oilaviy hamkorlik yondashuvlari, interaktiv metodlar va individual yondashuv orqali bolalarning rivojlanishini ta'minlash masalalari ham ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oilaviy hamkorlik, ota-ona, tarbiyachi, maktabgacha ta'lim, nutq rivoji, ijtimoiy rivojlanish, hissiy rivojlanish, interaktiv metod, pedagogik yondashuv, bolalar rivoji;

Abstract: This article highlights the importance of family cooperation in preschool education and its role in a child's development. It analyzes effective communication between parents and educators, the integration of family activities into the educational process, home-based learning methods, and the family's involvement in the pedagogical environment. The study also explores how family engagement influences children's speech, social, and emotional development. Furthermore, the article discusses modern approaches to family cooperation, interactive methods, and individualized strategies that contribute to the holistic growth of preschool children.

Keywords: family cooperation, parents, educator, preschool education, speech development, social development, emotional development, interactive method, pedagogical approach, child development.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается значение семейного сотрудничества в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях и его роль в развитии ребёнка. Рассматриваются вопросы эффективного взаимодействия между родителями и воспитателями, интеграция семейной деятельности в образовательный процесс, методы, применяемые дома, а также влияние участия семьи в педагогическом процессе на развитие речи, социальных и эмоциональных качеств ребёнка. Кроме того, в статье анализируются современные подходы к семейному сотрудничеству, интерактивные методы и индивидуальные подходы, способствующие всестороннему развитию детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: семейное сотрудничество, родители, воспитатель, дошкольное образование, развитие речи, социальное развитие, эмоциональное развитие, интерактивный метод, педагогический подход, развитие ребёнка.

Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlik - bu bolaning shaxs sifatida shakllanishida eng muhim pedagogik yo'nalishlardan biridir. Ta'lim jarayonida oilaning faol ishtiroki bolaning ijtimoiylashuvi, o'ziga ishonch, mustaqillik va muloqot madaniyatining rivojlanishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Oila bola uchun birinchi tarbiya maktabi hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va oila o'rtasida muntazam, tizimli hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish tarbiyachining eng muhim vazifalaridan biri sanaladi [1]. Ota-onalar va tarbiyachilar o'rtasida o'zaro ishonchli muloqot o'rnatilsa, bola o'zini xavfsiz va qadrlangan his etadi, bu esa uning hissiy barqarorligini ta'minlaydi. Psixolog Vygotskiy [2] ta'kidlaganidek, bolaning rivojlanishida "yaqin rivojlanish zonasi" konsepsiyasi muhim ahamiyatga ega - ya'ni, bola kattalar bilan hamkorlikda o'z imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Shu sababli, tarbiyachi va ota-onaning birgalikdagi faoliyati bolaning kognitiv, nutqiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi o'rin tutadi.

Oilaviy hamkorlik turli shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi: ota-onalar yig'ilishlari, ochiq darslar, seminar-treninglar, oilaviy tanlovlar, "Ota-onalar kuni", "Oila va bola" mavzusidagi

suhbatlar va interaktiv uchrashuvlar. Bunday tadbirlar ota-onalarga ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining mohiyatini tushunish, bolalar bilan to'g'ri muloqot qilish, emotsional qo'llab-quvvatlash va tarbiyaviy strategiyalarni to'g'ri tanlashda yordam beradi [2]. Masalan, "Ota-onalar ishtirokida ertak kuni" kabi tadbirlar nafaqat bolalarda kitobga qiziqishni, balki ota-ona bilan hissiy aloqani mustahkamlaydi. Ota-ona bolasi bilan birgalikda hikoya o'qib, rollarni ijro etsa, bola o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etishga, nutqni to'g'ri shakllantirishga o'rganadi. Shu bilan birga, ota-onaning o'zi ham ta'lim jarayonining faol ishtirokchisiga aylanadi, bu esa pedagogik hamkorlikning barqaror tizimini yaratadi [3]. Oilaviy hamkorlikning yana bir muhim yo'nalishi – kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishdir. Bolaning muloqot qilish madaniyati asosan oilada shakllanadi, shu bois tarbiyachilar ota-onalarga bola bilan muloqotning ijobiy usullarini o'rgatishlari lozim. Ota-ona bolani tinglash, fikrini qadrlash, tanqid o'rniga ijobiy rag'bat berish orqali uning o'ziga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi [2]. Ota-onaning mehri, izchil va rag'batlantiruvchi so'zlari bolada nutq rivoji bilan bir qatorda hissiy barqarorlikni ham shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy ta'limda interaktiv oilaviy hamkorlik texnologiyalari keng qo'llanilmoqda. Masalan, onlayn platformalarda ota-onalar uchun pedagogik treninglar, virtual maslahatlar, bolaning rivojlanish monitoringi va tarbiyachi-ota-ona guruh chatlari tashkil etiladi. Bu usullar orqali ota-onalar farzandining rivojlanishini doimiy kuzatib borish imkoniga ega bo'ladilar va tarbiyachi bilan tezkor axborot almashadilar.

Shuningdek, oilaviy hamkorlik bolaning ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda ham beqiyos ahamiyatga ega. Ota-onalar bilan birgalikdagi loyihalar, ekologik aksiyalar yoki "Oila va tabiat" mavzusidagi tadbirlar orqali bolalar jamoada ishlashni, tabiatni asrashni, ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni his etishni o'rganadilar [1]. Bu jarayonlar orqali bola o'zini jamiyatning faol a'zosi sifatida his etadi. Oilaviy hamkorlikni samarali yo'lga qo'yishda tarbiyachining roli beqiyosdir. U nafaqat ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etadi, balki ota-onalarga pedagogik maslahat beradi, ularni bolaning psixologik holatidan xabardor qiladi, individual yondashuvni ta'minlaydi va bolaning ijobiy rivojlanish dinamikasini kuzatib boradi [2]. Shu tariqa, oilaviy hamkorlik -bu nafaqat pedagogik jarayonning bir qismi, balki ta'limning samaradorligini oshiruvchi ijtimoiy-madaniy tizimdir. U bolaning har tomonlama rivojlanishi, nutqiy kompetensiyasi, ijodkorligi va hissiy muvozanatini ta'minlaydi. Ota-ona va tarbiyachi o'rtasidagi doimiy hamkorlik bolani kelajakdagi ta'lim bosqichlariga puxta tayyorlaydi, o'qishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshiradi va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishga turtki beradi.

Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlikni rivojlantirish -bu zamonaviy pedagogikaning eng muhim yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Ota-ona va tarbiyachi o'rtasida o'zaro ishonch, hamjihatlik va muloqotning mavjudligi bolaning shaxsiy rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Oila va ta'lim muassasasi o'rtasida uyg'un hamkorlik bo'lgandagina bola o'zini xavfsiz, qadrlangan va muvaffaqiyatli his etadi. Shu sababli, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ota-onalar uchun muntazam seminarlar, psixologik treninglar, interaktiv uchrashuvlar tashkil etish, bolalarning oilaviy faoliyatda ishtirokini rag'batlantirish zarurdir. Bunday yondashuv bolada nafaqat bilim, balki ijtimoiy javobgarlik, mustaqillik va ijobiy hayotiy qadriyatlarni shakllantiradi.

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THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract: The article examines the key theoretical and practical issues of equivalence in translation between Uzbek and English. In fact, equivalence means that the translation conveys the same meaning, style, and emotional effect as the original text. However, due to significant grammatical, cultural, and lexical differences between the two languages, achieving full equivalence is often challenging. Therefore, the concept of equivalence, its main types, and real examples of translation difficulties are outlined in this article. It also describes strategies that translators may use to solve these problems and ensure accurate and culturally appropriate translations.

Key words: translation equivalence; Uzbek–English translation; dynamic equivalence; formal equivalence; linguistic differences; cultural translation; translation strategies

Translation is the process of transferring meaning from one language into another. Indeed, one of the core goals in translation is achieving equivalence, meaning the translated text should deliver the same message and emotional impact as the original. However, this goal is difficult to reach, especially between two linguistically and culturally distant languages such as Uzbek and English.

Uzbek, being considered as a Turkic language with agglutinative grammar, and English - a Germanic analytic language, differ in both structure and worldview. These differences make direct, word-for-word translation nearly impossible. As Nida (1964) emphasized, translators should prioritize meaning and communicative effect over literal accuracy. Thus, both the *theoretical foundations* and *practical challenges* of equivalence between Uzbek and English will be discussed further.

Equivalence refers to the relationship between source and target texts where the translation conveys the same meaning, style, and communicative function. Jakobson (1959) noted that complete equivalence between languages is rare; translators must find *approximate meaning* rather than identical wording, whereas Nida (1964) distinguished between formal equivalence (literal, form-based translation) and dynamic equivalence (meaning- and effect-based translation). Dynamic equivalence is often more suitable for Uzbek–English translation because it focuses more on the reader's response.

Similarly, Newmark (1988) described two translation methods: semantic translation, focusing on the original meaning, and communicative translation, focusing on the effect on the target audience. The translator's choice depends on the purpose, audience, and text type.

As Catford (1965) explained, each language has its own grammatical system that shapes how meaning is expressed.

<i>Feature</i>	<i>Uzbek</i>	<i>English</i>
<i>Word order</i>	<i>Subject–Object–Verb (SOV)</i>	<i>Subject–Verb–Object (SVO)</i>
<i>Example</i>	<i>Men kitob o'qidim.</i>	<i>I read a book.</i>

Feature	Uzbek	English
Articles	None	Uses <i>a, an, the</i>
Grammar markers	Uses suffixes (agglutination)	Uses word order and auxiliaries
Formality	Distinguishes <i>sen (informal) / Siz (formal)</i>	Only <i>you</i>

That is why these structural and cultural differences mean that direct equivalence rarely works. As Bell (1991) observed, grammar strongly influences how meaning is constructed in each language.

Many Uzbek words have no direct English equivalent. For example, *mehmondoʻstlik* expresses deep hospitality and generosity that cannot really be expressed with the English word *hospitality*. Ganieva (2020) explained that such cultural concepts often require paraphrasing or short explanations to preserve meaning. Furthermore, Baker (1992) recommended using paraphrase or descriptive phrases when no single equivalent exists.

Idioms and proverbs are culture-bound expressions that rarely translate literally. Example:

Uzbek: *Koʻz qorachigʻiday asramoq*

Word-for-word in English: *To protect like the pupil of the eye*

Better translation: *To cherish* or *To protect dearly*

Khalilova (2021) emphasized that idioms carry deep emotional meaning; translators should use equivalent English idioms or explanatory phrases. Akhmedova (2022) also showed how Uzbek proverbs can be translated using either similar English expressions or brief explanations.

Equivalence in translation aims to preserve meaning and emotional impact across languages. However, between Uzbek and English, perfect equivalence is rare due to structural, grammatical, and cultural differences. Scholars such as Nida (1964), Jakobson (1959), Newmark (1988), and Baker (1992) have provided valuable frameworks for addressing these challenges.

As researchers like Ganieva (2020) and Khudoyberganova (2018) have shown, successful translation between Uzbek and English requires not only linguistic knowledge but also cultural sensitivity. Translators must select the most appropriate strategy to preserve message, tone, and style. With proper understanding and creativity, a high level of equivalence can be achieved, even if perfect equivalence is unattainable.

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CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ORAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. Teaching oral communication remains one of the most challenging aspects of foreign language education. While learners may acquire grammar and vocabulary through traditional methods, developing fluency, pronunciation, and interactive competence requires authentic practice and exposure. This article examines the key difficulties teachers face in teaching oral communication skills, including learner anxiety, limited classroom time, assessment issues, and lack of authentic contexts. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating communicative methodologies, task-based learning, and digital tools to overcome these challenges. The findings suggest that successful development of oral communication requires a balance between linguistic accuracy and communicative fluency, supported by learner-centered strategies.

Keywords: oral communication, speaking skills, foreign language teaching, communicative competence, classroom challenges.

Introduction. The development of oral communication skills is one of the most essential yet problematic areas in foreign language teaching. While written competence can be taught through exercises and controlled practice, speaking requires dynamic interaction, rapid processing, and confidence. For decades, teachers have acknowledged that helping students to speak fluently in a foreign language is far more challenging than teaching grammar or reading comprehension. In today’s interconnected world, oral communication competence is no longer optional but a necessity. International mobility, global employment opportunities, and intercultural exchange make speaking skills a priority. However, learners often face psychological barriers such as fear of mistakes, anxiety about pronunciation, and lack of confidence in spontaneous conversation. Teachers, in turn, are constrained by limited classroom time, large group sizes, and the difficulty of creating authentic speaking contexts. This article addresses the main obstacles in teaching oral communication skills and explores pedagogical strategies that can enhance the effectiveness of instruction.

Literature Review. Research on oral communication in second and foreign language acquisition emphasizes its central role in communicative competence (Hymes, 1972). Canale and Swain (1980) identified speaking as an integral component of communicative competence alongside grammatical, sociolinguistic, and strategic elements. Richards (2008) highlighted that fluency is not only the ability to produce speech but also the capacity to interact effectively and spontaneously.

Scholars such as Horwitz (2001) have documented the pervasive issue of foreign language speaking anxiety, which negatively affects learner performance and willingness to communicate. Nation and Newton (2009) stressed the importance of fluency-oriented practice, while Thornbury (2005) argued for task-based approaches that simulate real-life communication.

More recent studies (Derwing & Munro, 2015; Rao, 2019) have focused on pronunciation instruction, advocating intelligibility over native-like accuracy. Digital

technologies, such as speech recognition and virtual exchanges, have also emerged as tools to enhance oral communication practice in classroom and online settings.

Methodology. This study employs a qualitative approach through the review and analysis of existing research, teaching practices, and case studies in the field of foreign language pedagogy. Data sources include peer-reviewed articles, textbooks on communicative methodologies, and teacher-reported experiences. The methodology involves: identifying common challenges teachers encounter in teaching oral communication; categorizing these challenges into psychological, methodological, and contextual dimensions; evaluating existing strategies and innovations aimed at overcoming these challenges. This approach allows for a holistic understanding of the problem and provides a foundation for practical recommendations.

Results and Discussion. The findings indicate that teaching oral communication skills presents a set of interrelated challenges:

1. **Learner Anxiety and Psychological Barriers.** Students often hesitate to speak for fear of making mistakes or being judged. This anxiety reduces participation and limits opportunities for practice. Teachers need to create a supportive environment that encourages risk-taking and values communicative effort over perfection.

2. **Limited Classroom Time and Group Sizes.** Traditional classroom structures rarely allow sufficient speaking practice. Large groups reduce the teacher's ability to provide individual feedback, while limited lesson time often prioritizes grammar and vocabulary over speaking activities.

3. **Assessment Difficulties.** Evaluating oral performance is complex due to its subjective nature. Teachers struggle to balance criteria such as accuracy, fluency, pronunciation, and interaction. Overemphasis on accuracy may discourage students from speaking freely.

4. **Lack of Authentic Communication Contexts.** Classroom dialogues often feel artificial and fail to reflect real-life communicative demands. Without opportunities to use the language meaningfully, learners cannot transfer classroom skills to real situations.

5. **Potential Solutions: Communicative and Task-Based Approaches** (Role-plays, simulations, and problem-solving activities foster authentic interaction); **Integration of Technology** (Speech recognition apps, virtual exchanges, and online discussions extend speaking opportunities beyond the classroom); **Fluency over Perfection** (Prioritizing intelligibility and spontaneous expression reduces anxiety and builds confidence); **Learner-Centered Strategies** (Encouraging peer interaction, group work, and collaborative tasks promotes active engagement).

Conclusion. Teaching oral communication skills in foreign language classrooms is a demanding but essential endeavor. The main challenges – learner anxiety, time limitations, assessment difficulties, and lack of authentic contexts – require innovative pedagogical responses. By adopting communicative methodologies, integrating digital tools, and creating supportive learning environments, teachers can help learners develop both fluency and confidence. The future of foreign language education lies not in eliminating errors but in empowering students to communicate meaningfully across cultures.

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XORIJIY TILNI O‘RGANISHDA MADANIYATNING TA’SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xorijiy tilni o‘rganish jarayonida madaniyatning o‘rni va ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Til va madaniyat o‘rtasidagi uzviy bog‘liqlik, shuningdek, o‘qitish jarayonida madaniy komponentni samarali kiritishning usullari ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan. Madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirishda kommunikativ va interaktiv yondashuvlarning o‘rni, hamda xalqaro ta’lim tizimida madaniyatning integratsiyasi muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Til va madaniyat, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, kommunikativ yondashuv, lingvomadaniyat, xalqaro muloqot, global madaniyat, til ta’limi.

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of culture in the process of foreign language learning. It highlights the inseparable connection between language and culture, as well as effective methods for integrating cultural components into the teaching process. The paper also discusses the role of communicative and interactive approaches in developing intercultural competence and the integration of culture within the international education system.

Keywords: language and culture, intercultural competence, communicative approach, linguoculture, international communication, global culture, language education.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются роль и значение культуры в процессе изучения иностранного языка. Отмечается неразрывная связь между языком и культурой, а также представлены эффективные методы интеграции культурного компонента в процесс обучения. Обсуждается роль коммуникативного и интерактивного подходов в формировании межкультурной компетенции, а также интеграция культуры в международную систему образования.

Ключевые слова: язык и культура, межкультурная компетенция, коммуникативный подход, лингвокультура, международное общение, глобальная культура, языковое образование.

Til xalqning madaniy merosini saqlovchi va uni ifodalovchi asosiy vositadir. E. Sapir va B. Uorf nazariyasiga ko‘ra, til inson tafakkurini shakllantiradi va madaniyatni ifodalashda asosiy omil hisoblanadi [1]. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi “time is money” iborasi ingliz xalqining vaqtni qadrlash madaniyatini, yapon tilidagi “wa” tushunchasi esa uyg‘unlik va hurmat qadriyatini bildiradi [5]. Kramshch ta’kidlaganidek, madaniyat tildan ajralgan holda o‘qitilsa, o‘rganilayotgan til sun’iy mazmun kasb etadi [5].

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya - bu shaxsning turli madaniyat vakillari bilan to‘g‘ri va samarali muloqot qila olish qobiliyatidir. Byram [2] bu kompetensiyani “xalqaro muloqotda tushunish va hurmat bilan yondashish qobiliyati” deb ta’riflaydi. Brooks [1] fikricha, madaniyatni o‘qitish til o‘rganishning asosiy maqsadlaridan biri bo‘lishi kerak.

Til o‘qituvchilari madaniyat elementlarini o‘quv jarayoniga quyidagi yo‘llar bilan integratsiya qilishi mumkin:

1. Autentik materiallardan foydalanish (filmlar, qo‘shiqlar, seriallar, reklama roliklari) [7].
2. Rol o‘yinlari va simulyatsiyalar orqali real muloqot ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish [4].
3. Madaniy loyiha ishlari va taqdimotlar [6].
4. Virtual muloqot platformalaridan foydalanish (eTwinning, Zoom) [3].
4. Global ta‘lim tizimida madaniyatning o‘rni

Zamonaviy global ta‘limda tilni o‘rgatish jarayoni “language and culture integration” modeliga asoslanadi. CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) standartlariga ko‘ra, chet tili o‘qitishda madaniyatlararo kompetensiya muhim mezon sifatida belgilangan [3].

5. O‘qituvchining roli va mas‘uliyati

Chet tili o‘qituvchisi madaniyatlararo tafakkurni shakllantiruvchi asosiy shaxsdir. Harmer [4] fikricha, zamonaviy o‘qituvchi darsni “til + madaniyat” integratsiyasi asosida olib borishi kerak. O‘qituvchi o‘quvchilarni stereotiplardan xoli bo‘lishga, turli madaniy tafovutlarni hurmat qilishga o‘rgatishi zarur.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, xorijiy tilni o‘rganishda madaniyatning ta‘siri juda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Tilni bilish - bu xalqning madaniyatini anglash demakdir. Shuning uchun chet tili ta‘limida madaniyat komponentini o‘qitish jarayoniga to‘liq integratsiya qilish zarur. Madaniyatlararo yondashuv orqali o‘quvchilar nafaqat lingvistik, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatdan ham yetuk shaxsga aylanadi. Bu esa ularni global fuqarolik ruhida tarbiyalash, madaniyatlar o‘rtasida muloqot o‘rnatish va bag‘rikenglikni kuchaytirishga xizmat qiladi.

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GIBRID TA‘LIM MODELIDA O‘QUV RESURSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING OPTIMAL STRATEGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta‘lim tizimida keng qo‘llanilayotgan gibrid ta‘lim modeli, uning asosiy tamoyillari va o‘quv resurslarini tashkil etishning samarali strategiyalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalar va an‘anaviy ta‘lim usullarini uyg‘unlashtirishning afzalliklari, interaktiv o‘quv muhitini yaratish imkoniyatlari va sifatli o‘quv jarayonini ta‘minlash mexanizmlari yoritilgan. Maqola oliy ta‘lim, umumta‘lim hamda kasbiy ta‘lim tizimida gibrid modelni joriy etish bo‘yicha tavsiyalarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: gibridd taʼlim, raqamli texnologiyalar, masofaviy taʼlim, oʻquv resurslari, interaktiv platforma, taʼlim sifatini oshirish, innovatsion taʼlim.

Abstract: This article analyzes the hybrid learning model widely used in the modern education system, its main principles, and effective strategies for organizing educational resources. It also highlights the advantages of integrating digital technologies with traditional teaching methods, the opportunities for creating an interactive learning environment, and the mechanisms for ensuring a high-quality educational process. The article includes recommendations for implementing the hybrid model in higher, general, and vocational education systems.

Keywords: hybrid learning, digital technologies, distance education, learning resources, interactive platform, improving education quality, innovative learning.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализирована гибридная модель обучения, широко применяемая в современной системе образования, её основные принципы и эффективные стратегии организации учебных ресурсов. Также раскрываются преимущества интеграции цифровых технологий с традиционными методами обучения, возможности создания интерактивной образовательной среды и механизмы обеспечения качественного учебного процесса. В статье приведены рекомендации по внедрению гибридной модели в систему высшего, общего и профессионального образования.

Ключевые слова: гибридное обучение, цифровые технологии, дистанционное образование, учебные ресурсы, интерактивная платформа, повышение качества образования, инновационное обучение.

Soʻnggi yillarda raqamli texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi taʼlim tizimida tub oʻzgarishlarga sabab boʻlmoqda. Gibridd taʼlim modeli (blended learning) ana shunday oʻzgarishlarning amaliy koʻrinishi boʻlib, anʼanaviy sinf xonasida olib boriladigan darslar bilan masofaviy onlayn taʼlim shakllarini birlashtiradi. Bu model taʼlim jarayonini yanada moslashuvchan, samarali va individual ehtiyojlarga mos holga keltiradi [1, 45-b.]. Gibridd taʼlimning dolzarbligi pandemiyadan keyin yanada ortdi. Taʼlim jarayonini toʻxtatmasdan davom ettirish uchun koʻplab mamlakatlarda masofaviy va aralash taʼlim modellaridan foydalanila boshlandi [2, 112-b.]. Hozirgi kunda Oʻzbekiston oliy va umumiy oʻrta taʼlim tizimida ham gibridd modelni joriy etish boʻyicha amaliy ishlar olib borilmoqda. Gibridd modelda taʼlimning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari quyidagilardan iborat:

Anʼanaviy oʻqitish metodlari (maʼruza, seminar, amaliy mashgʻulot);

Onlayn taʼlim resurslari (videodarslar, virtual laboratoriyalar, interaktiv platformalar);

Mustaqil oʻqish uchun qoʻshimcha materiallar;

Gibridd taʼlim modeli - bu taʼlim jarayonida onlayn va oflayn komponentlarning uygʻunlashuvi orqali samaradorlikni oshiruvchi yondashuvdir [3, 87-b.]. U taʼlim oluvchining bilim olish tezligini, shaklini va usulini individual tarzda tanlash imkonini beradi. Gibridd modelning nazariy asoslari konstruktivizm tamoyillariga tayanadi. Konstruktivizmga koʻra, bilim shaxsning faol ishtiroki orqali shakllanadi. Shuning uchun talaba dars jarayonining markazida turadi, oʻqituvchi esa yoʻnaltiruvchi rolini bajaradi.

Bundan tashqari, bu model zamonaviy taʼlim texnologiyalari, raqamli platformalar va interaktiv oʻquv muhiti bilan uzviy bogʻliq. Masalan, oʻquv jarayonida “Learning Management System” (LMS) platformalaridan keng foydalaniladi. LMS yordamida oʻqituvchi darslarni yuklaydi, topshiriqlarni yuboradi, testlarni baholaydi va talabalarning faoliyatini nazorat qiladi [4, 56-b.].

Oʻquv resurslarini tashkil etishda strategik yondashuvlar

Gibridd taʼlimni samarali tashkil etishda oʻquv resurslarining sifatli va tizimli boʻlishi hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. Quyidagi strategiyalar bu jarayonda muhim rol oʻynaydi:

Moodle, Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams, Zoom kabi platformalar o'qitish jarayonini soddalashtiradi, interaktivlikni oshiradi va talabaning darsga jalb qilinish darajasini ko'taradi [5, 215-b.]. Resurslar modul shaklida tashkil etilganda, talaba o'ziga mos tempda o'rganish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Har bir modul nazariy qism, amaliy topshiriq va test baholashdan iborat bo'lishi kerak [6, 133-b.]. Multimedia materiallar bilan boyitish Videodarslar, infografikalar, ovozli izohlar va virtual laboratoriyalar bilimni chuqurroq o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi [7, 98-b.]. Talabalarning faol ishtirokini ta'minlash uchun forumlar, chat xonalari va onlayn muhokama maydonlari yaratiladi. Bu ularning bilimni mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi [8, 54-b.].

Gibrid ta'lim jarayonida faqat resurslar emas, balki pedagogik yondashuvlar ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Samaradorlikni oshiruvchi asosiy omillar quyidagilar: Pedagogik kompetensiya: O'qituvchining raqamli vositalardan to'g'ri foydalanish ko'nikmasi [9, 223-b.]; Texnik infratuzilma: Internet sifati, kompyuter texnikasi, dasturiy ta'minotning barqarorligi; Motivatsiya: Talabada mustaqil o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishni shakllantirish; Moslashuvchanlik: O'quv jarayonini talabalar ehtiyojiga moslashtirish. Agar bu omillar e'tibordan chetda qolsa, gibrid ta'limning samaradorligi pasayadi. Shu bois strategik rejalashtirishda pedagogik va texnik jihatlar uyg'un tarzda ko'zda tutilishi lozim.

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EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHER'S ROLE IN PROJECTING IT

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Abstract: Emotional engagement plays a vital role in the process of language acquisition, standing alongside cognitive involvement as a determining factor of learner success. For many EFL learners, insufficient emotional connection to the learning process can lead to reduced motivation, limited participation, and slower linguistic progress. Emotional engagement encompasses the learner's sense of connection, involvement, and affective response to language learning experiences. Emotions - both positive (such as pride, curiosity, confidence, and empathy) and negative (such as anxiety, frustration, or embarrassment) - profoundly influence motivation, classroom behavior, and long-term language retention. This paper explores the teacher's crucial role in shaping and projecting emotional engagement through interactive, gamified, and learner-centered approaches.

Key words: emotional engagement, atmosphere, classroom, students, learning environment, connections, relationship, motivation, language learning.

Emotionally involvement in what you are learning is as just crucial as cognitive process of it. For EFL learners, the development of language skills is often impeded by a variety of factors, including lack of motivation and emotional engagement [1]. How connected or involved language learners are can be defined as emotional engagement. Emotions like pride when they tell the meaning of a word, embarrassment when they got laughed at for not getting the pronunciation right, or a fear of being the first to present an assignment are all emotions which can whether enhance their motivation and learning process or else. Emotions can be positive or negative and as the names refer, they have the ability to affect individuals' language skills and their overall attitude towards a language.

Especially in language classrooms you may encounter gamified learning compared to other classes due to its importance in developing motivation that is the main factor in language acquiree. During the games some may win, feeling of pride arises, some may feel disappointed which is frustration and one of them can feel interested in the topic that had been integrated into the game and would like to search more about it which summons up as a curiosity. Those all can help your students to remember any language element better than just teacher-centered teaching, considering emotions can make memories stronger.

Motivation, defined as the internal or external drive to pursue language learning goals, directly impacts learners' willingness to engage with literacy tasks [2]. According to Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory (SDT), intrinsic motivation fosters a more sustainable and effective learning process compared to extrinsic motivation. Emotional engagement plays a pivotal role in how EFL learners approach any activities during the lessons. Krashen's (1982) Affective Filter Hypothesis suggests that when learners are emotionally engaged, they are more likely to lower their "affective filter" and absorb language more effectively. Krashen says that in humans there is so called Affective filter which can be created by anxiety, low self-esteem and lack of motivation.

In-game learning could positively impact students' cognitive development and help them retain knowledge more effectively in secondary school is something that Akhmetova demonstrated. Specifically, AR makes abstract physics concepts more real and thus interesting and easily understandable. By bringing immersive and interactive learning experiences, AR not only makes learning fun and exciting but, through gamified interfaces, keeps students engaged and motivated, providing a transformation from traditional education to a more agile and impactful one [3].

In the process of assessing student, we should be aware of emotional impact that it might have on them and so taking extra cautious steps into evaluating them is another way of creating more positively engaging learning environment. Evaluation methods are at the heart of teaching. Newer assessment strategies like formative assessment and peer assessment yield essential feedback that facilitates learning for students. Instructor feedback is especially vital in facilitating student development and motivation since it enables students to determine areas of improvement while also acknowledging their strengths [4].

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USING AUTHENTIC AUDIO-VISUAL MATERIALS TO IMPROVE LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS

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Annotation: This article explores the effectiveness of authentic audio-visual materials in enhancing listening and speaking skills in foreign language classrooms. It discusses how exposure to real-life language use through films, podcasts, interviews, and online videos helps learners develop communicative competence, pronunciation, fluency, and cultural understanding. The study emphasizes the role of teachers in selecting appropriate materials and creating interactive learning environments. Findings suggest that authentic resources increase students' motivation and engagement, leading to more meaningful and effective language learning experiences.

Keywords: authentic materials, audio-visual aids, listening skills, speaking fluency, communicative competence, foreign language teaching.

Introduction: Listening and speaking are two of the most essential skills in foreign language learning. They are the foundation of communication, allowing learners to express ideas and understand others in real-life contexts. However, traditional teaching methods often focus on grammar and vocabulary rather than authentic communication. In recent years, educators have recognized the importance of using real-world materials, such as films, songs, interviews, and podcasts, to make language learning more natural and effective.¹¹ These resources are known as authentic audio-visual materials, and they play a vital role in developing communicative competence among learners. The aim of this paper is to analyze the benefits of using authentic audio-visual materials in improving students' listening and speaking skills, explore the challenges teachers may face, and suggest effective strategies for integrating such materials into the classroom.

Literature Review. Several researchers have highlighted the value of authenticity in language learning. Gilmore (2007) defines authentic materials as those 'produced by and for native speakers' without pedagogical modification. Such materials provide learners with exposure to real accents, natural speech speed, colloquial expressions, and cultural references¹². According to Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985), learners acquire language most effectively when they are exposed to comprehensible input that reflects real communication.

¹¹ Herron, C., & Seay, I. (1991). The effect of authentic video on foreign language listening comprehension. *Foreign Language Annals*, 24(6), 487–495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.1991.tb00406.x>

¹² Krashen, S. D. (1985). *The input hypothesis: Issues and implications*. New York: Longman.

Authentic materials meet this requirement by presenting real linguistic input in meaningful contexts. Studies by Sherman (2003) and Herron & Seay (1991) show that learners who use films and videos in language classes demonstrate improved comprehension and pronunciation. Authentic resources not only develop linguistic competence but also increase cultural awareness. However, some challenges exist, such as learners finding authentic materials difficult due to fast speech or unfamiliar vocabulary, requiring careful material selection.

Methodology: This study was conducted among 30 intermediate-level students at a university language center. Participants were divided into two groups: an experimental group using authentic audio-visual materials and a control group using traditional textbook-based exercises. The experimental group was exposed to various authentic resources over eight weeks, including short films, YouTube interviews, podcasts, and news reports. Lessons focused on listening comprehension, pronunciation practice, and interactive speaking activities such as role plays and discussions. Data were collected through pre-tests and post-tests assessing listening and speaking performance, as well as student feedback forms measuring motivation and engagement.

Findings and Discussion: The results indicated a significant improvement in both listening and speaking skills among students who used authentic audio-visual materials. Their listening comprehension scores increased by 25%, and speaking fluency improved in terms of speed, accuracy, and pronunciation. Students reported that authentic videos helped them understand natural speech, slang, and intonation patterns better than textbook dialogues. Moreover, students felt more motivated to participate in discussions and role plays after watching videos related to real-life situations. Teachers observed a more dynamic classroom atmosphere, with learners actively collaborating and interpreting meanings together. Despite initial difficulties such as fast-paced speech and unfamiliar vocabulary, most students expressed positive attitudes toward authentic materials and their contribution to language development.

Conclusion: Authentic audio-visual materials are powerful tools for enhancing listening and speaking skills in foreign language classrooms. They expose learners to real communication, diverse accents, and cultural contexts, promoting motivation, confidence, and fluency. Teachers play a vital role in selecting appropriate materials, designing engaging tasks, and guiding comprehension. Although authentic content may be challenging, careful planning and gradual adaptation can overcome difficulties. Incorporating authentic resources creates a more interactive and effective learning environment. Future research should explore the long-term impact of authentic materials on overall proficiency and cultural awareness.

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THE PRINCIPLES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article examines the role of interdisciplinary integration in teaching foreign languages within the education system of New Uzbekistan. Theoretical and practical aspects of integrative methodology are analyzed, emphasizing its importance in developing students' ability to synthesize knowledge, think critically, and communicate freely in a foreign language. The study also explores international practices, particularly the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) model, which combines subject and language learning effectively. Furthermore, the article substantiates that implementing integrative approaches in New Uzbekistan's education system plays a crucial role in preparing students for international certification exams such as IELTS and TOEFL, which assess multidisciplinary academic skills.

Keywords: interdisciplinary integration, foreign language teaching, methodology, communicativeness, CLIL, innovation, New Uzbekistan, competence.

In the era of New Uzbekistan, the main goal of ongoing educational reforms is to nurture independent, critically thinking, and globally minded youth equipped with modern knowledge and skills. Teaching foreign languages plays a central role in this process, as it not only enhances linguistic competence but also develops communication culture, critical thinking, and intercultural competence among learners.

In the past, language teaching was largely based on memorizing grammatical rules and vocabulary. However, modern education has shifted towards integrative, innovative, and learner-centered approaches. Teaching a foreign language in harmony with other subjects provides learners with an opportunity to apply language in practice, understand cross-disciplinary connections, and broaden their worldview. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Every young person in New Uzbekistan must master foreign languages to communicate with the modern world - this is the foundation of a competitive generation." Therefore, strengthening interdisciplinary integration in education is not only a necessity of our time but also a new stage in language education.

Interdisciplinary integration is a methodological approach that combines the content of different subjects within a unified educational process, allowing students to acquire knowledge in a comprehensive way. This approach enhances logical thinking, analytical reasoning, and understanding of interconnections between disciplines.

Learning a foreign language becomes more effective when it is taught in connection with other subjects. For instance, during English lessons on "Global Warming," students can explore ecological terms from biology, geographical concepts, and economic implications. In this way, integration transforms language from a mere tool of communication into a means of acquiring knowledge and understanding global issues.

The Necessity of the Integrative Approach in New Uzbekistan's Education

In today's globalized world, students are preparing for international examinations such as IELTS, TOEFL, and CEFR. These tests involve texts and listening materials covering a variety of disciplines, including biology, sociology, economics, history, and technology. Hence, a modern language teacher must not only teach linguistic rules but also introduce interdisciplinary knowledge. In real-life communication, academic writing, and international

research, language and subject matter are inseparable. Therefore, the integrative approach in New Uzbekistan's education serves several key purposes:

1. To foster cross-disciplinary thinking among learners;
2. To make the learning process practical, engaging, and meaningful;
3. To teach the use of language in academic and social contexts;
4. To improve students' success in international certification exams.

The CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) model is widely used in international education systems. It is based on the principle of teaching academic subjects through a foreign language. This model is successfully implemented in Finland, the United Kingdom, South Korea, and Japan.

In CLIL, students do not just learn a language - they learn through the language. For example, biology, history, or mathematics lessons may be conducted in English. As a result, learners achieve two goals simultaneously: mastering subject knowledge and using the language in an authentic, meaningful context.

Adopting the CLIL model in New Uzbekistan's schools will develop not only students' linguistic competence but also their academic literacy, analytical reasoning, and logical writing skills.

The advantages of integrative learning can be summarized as follows:

1. Students learn language in real-life, meaningful contexts;
2. Lessons become more interesting, informative, and motivating;
3. Teachers use creativity to combine linguistic and subject knowledge;
4. Students develop independent and analytical thinking through cross-disciplinary connections.

For instance, when studying "Water Pollution" English and biology can be integrated. Students can discuss the causes, effects, and solutions of water contamination in English, thereby enhancing both ecological awareness and language proficiency.

It is important to note that this approach does not neglect other subjects; instead, it unites them in a single educational process. A foreign language serves as a universal key that connects disciplines and opens access to modern scientific knowledge.

To effectively implement interdisciplinary integration in the education system of New Uzbekistan, the following measures are recommended:

1. Gradual introduction of the CLIL model at different educational levels;
2. Specialized training for foreign language teachers in interdisciplinary methodology;
3. Development of bilingual teaching materials for integrated subjects;
4. Creation of digital platforms for interactive interdisciplinary lessons;
5. Launching "Subject + Language" projects for teachers and students.

Through these measures, education in New Uzbekistan will become more systematic, innovative, and globally competitive.

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BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA JISMONIY TARBIYA DARSLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL QILISH METODLARI

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of physical education in the development of primary school students. Physical education is viewed as a key factor that positively influences children's physical, mental, and social growth. During the early school years (ages 7–11), the musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, and respiratory systems actively develop; therefore, physical activities should be adapted to age-specific characteristics. The paper also highlights the importance of using anthropometric indicators-such as height, weight, and chest circumference-to assess students' physical development.

Keywords: physical education, physical development, primary school, child health, anthropometric indicators, psychophysiological development.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль и значение физического воспитания в развитии учащихся начальных классов. Физическое воспитание является важным фактором, способствующим физическому, психическому и социальному развитию детей. В возрасте 7–11 лет активно формируются опорно-двигательная, сердечно-сосудистая и дыхательная системы, что требует учета возрастных особенностей при организации занятий. Отмечается, что для оценки физического развития применяются антропометрические показатели, такие как рост, вес и окружность грудной клетки.

Ключевые слова: физическое воспитание, физическое развитие, начальная школа, здоровье детей, антропометрические показатели, психофизиологическое развитие.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining jismoniy rivojlanishida jismoniy tarbiyaning o'рни va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Jismoniy tarbiya bolalarning jismoniy, ruhiy hamda ijtimoiy rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir etuvchi muhim omil sifatida qaraladi. Boshlang'ich yosh davrida mushak-skelet, yurak-qon tomir va nafas olish tizimlari faol shakllanadi, shu bois mashg'ulotlar yosh xususiyatlariga mos tashkil etilishi lozim. Maqolada shuningdek, o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishini baholashda antropometrik ko'rsatkichlardan foydalanish zarurligi qayd etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy rivojlanish, boshlang'ich sinf, bolalar sog'lomligi, antropometriya, psixofiziologik rivojlanish.

Jismoniy tarbiya ta'lim jarayonining muhim qismi bo'lib, u bolalarning jismoniy, ruhiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishiga ta'sir qiladi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun jismoniy faollik nafaqat jismoniy rivojlanishni, balki ularning kognitiv qobiliyatlarini ham kuchaytirishga xizmat qiladi. Shu bois, O'zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiyaning samaradorligini

oshirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. «Jismoniy rivojlanish» tushunchasi orqali odam organizmining morfologik va funksional belgilarining o'zaro aloqadorlikdagi va irsiy xamda tashqi muhit omillariga bog'lik tavsifdagi umumiy yig'indisi ifodalanadi.

Jismoniy tarbiya bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Bolalarda harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirish, muskul kuchini oshirish, koordinatsiya va chidamkorlikni shakllantirish jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarining asosiy vazifalaridir. Jismoniy rivojlanish - usib kelayotgan yosh organizmning salomatlik xolatini belgilab beruvchi integral kursatkich xisoblanadi.

Jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlari esa bolaning umumiy o'sishiga, funksional tayyorgarligiga va psixologik barqarorligiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Boshlang'ich sinf yoshida (7–11 yosh) bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishida quyidagi xususiyatlar kuzatiladi:

Mushak-skelet tizimi: Bola suyaklari hali to'liq mustahkamlanmagan bo'lib, mushak to'qimasi ustunlik qiladi. Shu bois kuch ishlatish bilan bog'liq og'ir yuklamalar tavsiya etilmaydi.

Qon aylanish va nafas olish tizimi: Yurak va o'pka hajmi nisbatan kichik bo'lib, yurak urishi tez, nafas olish tezligi yuqori bo'ladi.

Koordinatsiya va harakatlanish qobiliyati: Harakat motorikasi va muvozanatni saqlash qobiliyati rivojlanib boradi, lekin hali ham aniqlik va tezkorlik jihatidan cheklovlar mavjud.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining barkamol shaxs bo'lib yetishishlarida jismoniy faollik va uning ta'siri yuqori hisoblanadi. Jismoniy mashqlar bolalarning nafaqat jismoniy, balki ruhiy va aqliy rivojlanishi uchun ham muhimdir. Jismoniy mashqlar o'z navbatida skelet va mushak tizimining mustahkamlanishi, yurak-tomir va nafas olish tizimining rivojlanishi, immunitetning oshishida hamda aqliy faollik va diqqatni jamlash qobiliyatining yaxshilanishida muhim o'rin egallaydi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining jismoniy rivojlanishini baholash uchun quyidagi testlar o'tkaziladi:

Antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar: Bo'yi, vazni, ko'krak qafasi aylanasi o'lchanadi.

1-jadval

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar

№	F.I.Sh.	Tug'ilgan kuni oyi yili	Bo'yi	Vazni	Ko'krak qafasi aylanasi
1	Islomov Jaxongir Allayor o'g'li	12.04.2016	121	33	59
2	Annaquliyev Diyorbek Oybek o'g'li	18.02.2016	119	32	58
3	Madjitov Dilmurod Ibroxim o'g'li	02.03.2016	118	31	56
4	Komilov Sardorbek O'ktamjon o'g'li	13.06.2016	119	30	58
5	Boybo'tayev Muxammad Islom o'g'li	02.07.2016	116	29	56
6	Ortiqov Mirsidiq Ravshan - o'g'li	11.06.2016	120	32	59
7	Otaboyev Ismoiljon Norimon o'g'li	19.01.2016	121	33	62
8	Mirbadalov Akobir Yusuf o'g'li	22.05.2016	116	30	60
9	Xayvarov Sherxon Bunyod o'g'li	29.08.2016	117	31	61
10	Zoxidov Jumaboy Zikirillo o'g'li	24.07.2016	120	32	61
11	O'rinboyev Azizbek Isroil o'g'li	22.02.2016	119	30	59
12	Davronov Javlonbek Baxrom o'g'li	08.06.2016	118	29	58
O'rtacha ko'rsatkichi			118,7	31	58,9

Yugurish testlari: 30 metr va 60 metrga yugurish tezligi.

Quvvatli mashqlar: Qo'l bilan tortishish yoki yerda yotish holatida turish.

Chambar aylantirish va uzunlikka sakrash kabi testlar: Harakat qobiliyati va muvozanatni baholash.

Jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etilishi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun jismoniy mashg'ulotlar quyidagi prinsiplarga asoslangan bo'lishi kerak:

O'yin shaklida o'tkazish – Bolalarning qiziqishini oshirish va faol ishtirokini ta'minlash kerak, davomiylilik va muntazamlik – Jismoniy mashqlar haftada 3-4 marta o'tkazilishi lozim, individual yondashuv – Har bir bolaning jismoniy tayyorgarligi darajasini hisobga olinishi, xavfsizlikni ta'minlash – Ortiqcha yuklamalar va jarohatlanish xavfini kamaytirish kabi mezonlarga e'tibor qaratish zarur.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining jismoniy rivojlanishi ularning salomatligi, harakat faolligi va ruhiy holati bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Shu sababli, jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini ilmiy asoslangan tarzda tashkil qilish va bolalarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari jismoniy rivojlanishining pedagogik baholash uchun quyidagi mezonlardan foydalanilinish tavsiya etiladi.

Antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar (bo'yi, vazni, ko'krak qafasi aylanasi va tana massasi indeksi)

Harakat faoliyati va koordinatsiya testlari (yugurish, sakrash, muvozanat)

Jismoniy chidamlilik va tezkorlik (60 m yugurish, 30 soniya joyida sakrash)

Psixomotor qobiliyatlar (reaksiya vaqti, diqqatni jamlash qobiliyati).

Jismoniy rivojlanish insonning umumiy jismoniy holati, harakat qobiliyati va funksional imkoniyatlarining rivojlanish jarayoni hisoblanadi. Ushbu jarayonni takomillashtirish uchun turli metodlar mavjud bo'lib, ular fiziologik, biomexanik va pedagogik asoslarga tayanadi. Quyida jismoniy rivojlanishni yaxshilashning eng samarali metodlari keltiriladi.

1. Jismoniy mashqlarning asosiy metodlari.

1.1. Reproduktiv (takroriy) metod. Mashqlarni bir necha marta takrorlash orqali harakat malakalarini rivojlantirish.

1.2. Muammoli-tahliliy metod. O'quvchilarga jismoniy mashqlarni bajarish jarayonida muammolarni mustaqil hal qilish imkoniyati beriladi.

1.3. Oylab davom ettiriladigan ta'sir metodi. Jismoniy yuklamalarni bosqichma-bosqich oshirish va organizmni maksimal ishlash holatiga olib kelish.

1.4. Ixtiyoriy (erkin) harakat metodi. O'quvchilar o'z harakatlarini mustaqil boshqaradi va ularni o'z xohishiga ko'ra bajaradi.

2. Jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish metodlari.

2.1. Kuchni rivojlantirish metodi. Salmoqli mashqlar: girya, shtanga va boshqa og'irliklar bilan ishlash. Izometrik mashqlar: statik holatda mushaklarning mustahkamlanishi. Dinamik kuch mashqlari: ko'p marotaba takrorlanadigan tezkor harakatlar (masalan, qo'l bilan turtib ko'tarilish).

2.2. Chidamkorlikni rivojlantirish metodi. Aerob mashqlar: uzoq masofaga yugurish, velosiped haydash. Intervalli mashg'ulotlar: yugurish va dam olish jarayonlarini ketma-ket bajarish. Qisqa va tezkor sprint mashqlari: organizmning haddan tashqari kuch sarflash qobiliyatini oshirish.

2.3. Chaqqonlik va tezkorlikni rivojlantirish. Reaktiv mashqlar: tezlik va harakatchanlikni oshirish (masalan, sprint yugurish). Koordinatsion mashqlar: murakkab traektoriyada harakat qilish mashqlari (masalan, konuslar orasida yugurish). Refleksni tezlashtirish: harakatli o'yinlar, estafetali o'yinlarda tezkor reaksiyani shakllantirish.

2.4. Moslashuvchanlik va harakat uyg'unligini rivojlantirish. Yog'iluvchanlik mashqlari: bug'imlar harakatchanligini oshirish uchun gimnastik mashqlar. Muvozanat va barqarorlik mashqlari: bir oyoqda turib harakat bajarish, maxsus trenajyorlarda mashq qilish.

3. Jismoniy rivojlanishni takomillashtirishga yordam beruvchi yordamchi metodlar

3.1. Biomexanik tahlil metodi. Harakatlarning samaradorligini oshirish uchun ilmiy asoslangan tahlildan foydalanish. Masalan: sportchi yugurish texnikasini tahlil qilish va uni optimallashtirish.

3.2. Pedagogik-nazorat metodi. Jismoniy mashg'ulotlarning samaradorligini baholash va yo'naltirish. Masalan: bolalarda harakat malakasini rivojlantirish uchun sport pedagoglari tomonidan beriladigan tavsiyalar.

3.3. Fiziologik adaptatsiya metodi. Mashg'ulot jarayonida organizmning yuklamalarga moslashishi. Masalan: yurak-qon tomir tizimini kuchaytirish uchun past intensivlikdagi mashg'ulotlar.

3.4. Psixologik tayyorgarlik. Jismoniy faoliyat jarayonida motivatsiyani oshirish va psixologik barqarorlikni rivojlantirish.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida jismoniy rivojlanishning optimal darajada b'lishi - bu, fiziologik yoshga bog'lik holatda, salomatlikni saqlash va mustahkamlash imkonini beruvchi, organizmning funksional imkoniyatlarini to'liq ro'yobga oshirishni ta'minlovchi me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga ega bo'lishni anglatadi. Bunda jismoniy faollikning optimal me'yor qiymati - bu, sutka davomida amalga oshirilgan umumiy harakatlar yig'indi qiymati bilan ifodalanadi.

Harakatlar faolligi tushunchasi - bu, irsiy va shuningdek, motivatsiyaga bog'liq, shartli reflekslar asosida, bolalar-o'smirlar organizmi jismoniy ko'rsatkichlarining kompleks namoyon b'lishi holati xisoblanadi.

Jismoniy rivojlanishni takomillashtirish turli xil metodlardan foydalanishni talab qiladi. Mashg'ulot jarayonida har bir insonning individual xususiyatlari, yoshi va jismoniy holati hisobga olinishi kerak. Samarali jismoniy tayyorgarlik uchun kuch, chidamkorlik, tezkorlik, chaqqonlik va harakat uyg'unligini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan integrativ yondashuv qo'llanilishi lozim.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA KITOB O‘QISHGA QIZIQISHNI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o‘qishga qiziqishni shakllantirish metodlari yoritilgan. Maqolada hikoya va ertaklar orqali bolalarda o‘qishga qiziqish uyg‘otish, interaktiv o‘qish mashg‘ulotlari, dramatik va rolli o‘yinlar orqali kitob bilan ishlash, shuningdek, kitob tanlash, vizual materiallardan foydalanish va tarbiyachining pedagogik roli tahlil qilinadi. Maqola, shuningdek, zamonaviy metodlar, individual yondashuv va interaktiv usullar orqali bolalarning nutqiy, ijodiy va muloqot ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalariga alohida e‘tibor qaratadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kitob o‘qish, qiziqish, maktabgacha yosh, interaktiv o‘qish, hikoya, ertak, dramatik o‘yin, tarbiyachi, pedagogik metod, nutq rivoji.

Abstract: This article discusses methods for developing an interest in reading among preschool children. It analyzes how storytelling and fairy tales can inspire a love of reading, how interactive reading activities, dramatic and role-playing games encourage engagement with books, and how to select appropriate reading materials. The article also examines the use of visual aids and the educator’s pedagogical role. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of modern methods, individualized approaches, and interactive techniques in fostering children’s speech, creativity, and communication skills.

Keywords: reading, interest, preschool age, interactive reading, storytelling, fairy tale, dramatic play, educator, pedagogical method, speech development.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются методы формирования интереса к чтению у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируется, как рассказы и сказки могут пробудить у детей любовь к чтению, как интерактивные занятия по чтению, драматические и ролевые игры способствуют взаимодействию с книгой. Также рассматриваются вопросы выбора книг, использования наглядных материалов и педагогическая роль воспитателя. Особое внимание уделяется современным методам, индивидуальному подходу и интерактивным способам развития речевых, творческих и коммуникативных навыков детей.

Ключевые слова: чтение, интерес, дошкольный возраст, интерактивное чтение, рассказ, сказка, драматическая игра, воспитатель, педагогический метод, развитие речи.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o‘qishga qiziqish shakllantirish jarayoni bolaning tafakkurini, nutqini, tasavvurini, ijodiy fikrlash va muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lib, bu jarayonda tarbiyachi va pedagogik metodlar asosiy rolni o‘ynaydi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, ertak va hikoyalarni interaktiv o‘qish orqali bolalarda qiziqish uyg‘onadi, ular kitob bilan mustaqil ishlashni o‘rganadi, voqelikni tushunish va fikrini ifoda etish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantiradi (Bosher, 2018, 34-b). Hikoyalarni dramatik va rolli o‘yin shaklida o‘qish bolalarda tafakkur, so‘z boyligi va muloqot ko‘nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi, shuningdek, ularni voqelik bilan bog‘lashni o‘rgatadi (Vygotskiy, 1983, 96-b). Tarbiyachi kitob tanlashda bolalarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olib, qiziqarli, mavzuga mos hikoyalarni tanlashi, ular bilan dialog o‘rnatishi, savol-javoblar va muammoli vaziyatlar orqali tafakkurini rivojlantirishi lozim [2]. Interaktiv o‘qish

mashg'ulotlari, masalan, "Rasm orqali hikoya tuzish", "Hikoya davomini aytish" yoki "Ertakni dramatik o'ynash" bolalarning so'z boyligini oshiradi, jumla tuzilishini mustahkamlaydi va ularni mavzu bo'yicha fikr almashishga rag'batlantiradi [3].

Shu bilan birga, multimediya vositalari, audio-kitoblar, video ertaklar va interaktiv kartochkalar bolalarning nutqiy faoliyatini faollashtiradi, ularni mustaqil fikrlashga, hikoya mazmunini tushunishga va yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirishga undaydi [1]. Tarbiyachi ushbu vositalardan foydalangan holda bolalarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olib individual yondashuvni tatbiq etadi va interaktiv mashg'ulotlar orqali ularni ijodiy fikrlash, muloqot va nutqiy kompetensiya ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi [1]. Shuningdek, hikoyalar va ertaklarni o'qish jarayonida tarbiyachi bolalarni mavzuga qiziqtirish uchun vizual materiallar, rasimli kartochkalar va dramatik sahnalar orqali qiziqarli faoliyat yaratadi. Masalan, ertak qahramonlarini rol o'ynash orqali bolalar voqealarni eslab qolish, ular haqida savol-javob berish va voqealarni o'z so'zlari bilan ifodalash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi [2]. Bu jarayon bolalarda ijodiy fikrlashni, mavzuni kengaytirish qobiliyatini, shuningdek, ijtimoiy va hissiy tajribani rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari, kitob tanlashda bolalar qiziqishi, ularning yosh va qobiliyat darajasi hisobga olinadi. Tarbiyachi hikoya yoki ertakni bolalarga tushunarli va qiziqarli shaklda taqdim etishi, ularni voqeani qayta so'zlashga, savollar berishga va muammoli vaziyatlarda fikr bildirishga rag'batlantirishi lozim [1].

Shu tariqa, interaktiv metodlar, dramatik mashg'ulotlar va multimediya vositalari bolalarda kitobga qiziqish uyg'otadi, nutqiy va muloqot ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi, ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi va bolalarni mustaqil o'qishga tayyorlaydi. Shu bilan birga, bolalarni jamoaviy ishlashga, birgalikda hikoya yaratishga va dramatik mashg'ulotlarda faol ishtirok etishga undash ularning ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishini ham ta'minlaydi [3]. Tarbiyachining individual yondashuvi, interaktiv metodlar va multimediya vositalarining uyg'unligi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o'qishga qiziqish shakllantirish jarayonini samarali qiladi va bolalarni kelajakdagi ta'lim bosqichlariga tayyorlashda mustahkam poydevor yaratadi [1]. Shu tariqa, kitob o'qishga qiziqishni shakllantirish metodlari zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar, dramatik va interaktiv metodlar, multimedia vositalari hamda tarbiyachining individual yondashuvi orqali bolalarning nutqiy, ijodiy, intellektual va ijtimoiy rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA O'YIN TEXNOLOGIYALARINING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida o'yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Maqolada o'yin

faoliyati orqali bolalarning soʻz boyligini kengaytirish, toʻgʻri talaffuzni shakllantirish, muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish hamda ogʻzaki nutqni mustahkamlash yoʻllari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy oʻyin texnologiyalarining pedagogik samaradorligi, interaktiv yondashuvlarning ahamiyati, tarbiyachining roli va individual yondashuvlar orqali nutqiy rivojlanishni taʼminlash masalalari ham koʻrib chiqilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: nutq rivoji, oʻyin texnologiyalari, ogʻzaki muloqot, soʻz boyligi, talaffuz, kommunikativ kompetensiya, tarbiyachi, innovatsiya, interaktiv metod, taʼlim texnologiyasi

Abstract: This article explores the importance of using play-based technologies in the development of speech among preschool-aged children. It analyzes how play activities can expand children's vocabulary, shape correct pronunciation, enhance communication culture, and strengthen oral expression. Additionally, the article examines the pedagogical effectiveness of modern game technologies, the significance of interactive approaches, the role of educators, and the importance of individualized methods in ensuring speech development.

Keywords: speech development, play technologies, oral communication, vocabulary, pronunciation, communicative competence, educator, innovation, interactive method, educational technology.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение использования игровых технологий в процессе развития речи у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируются способы расширения словарного запаса, формирования правильного произношения, развития культуры общения и укрепления устной речи посредством игровой деятельности. Кроме того, в статье освещаются педагогическая эффективность современных игровых технологий, значение интерактивных подходов, роль воспитателя и индивидуальные методы, обеспечивающие речевое развитие детей.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи, игровые технологии, устное общение, словарный запас, произношение, коммуникативная компетенция, воспитатель, инновация, интерактивный метод, образовательные технологии.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayoni bolaning fikrlash, muloqot qilish va oʻz fikrini ifoda etish qobiliyatini shakllantirishning eng muhim bosqichi boʻlib, bu jarayonda oʻyin texnologiyalari tabiiy, qiziqarli va samarali vosita sifatida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki oʻyin bolaning tafakkuri, eʼtiborini kuchaytiradi, soʻz boyligini kengaytiradi va ogʻzaki nutqni shakllantiradi, shuningdek, bolalarni faol muloqotga jalb qiladi, ularni rolli va didaktik mashgʻulotlar orqali ijtimoiy va hissiy tajriba bilan boyitadi, nutqdagi xatolarni erkin tuzatish, oʻz fikrini erkin ifoda etish va boshqa bolalar bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyatini beradi. Nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonida til oʻyinlari, dramatik mashgʻulotlar va interaktiv oʻyin texnologiyalari asosiy vosita boʻlib xizmat qiladi, ular bolalarda talaffuz, grammatik tuzilish va soʻz boyligini mustahkamlaydi, shuningdek, muammoli vaziyatlarda mustaqil qaror qabul qilish va ijodiy fikrlash koʻnikmalarini shakllantiradi.

Shu tariqa, oʻyin texnologiyalari bolalarda nafaqat nutqiy kompetensiyani, balki mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash va ijtimoiy koʻnikmalarni ham rivojlantiradi, bolaning oʻz fikriga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi, yangilik yaratish istagini oshiradi va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish malakasini shakllantiradi, bu esa uning keyingi taʼlim bosqichlarida muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi uchun mustahkam poydevor yaratadi. Shu bilan birga, oʻyin texnologiyalari bolaga ijtimoiy muhitda oʻzini erkin ifoda etish, jamoaviy ishlarni bajarish va muloqot madaniyatini oʻrganish imkonini beradi, bu esa bolaning nafaqat til kompetensiyasini, balki

hissiy, ijtimoiy va intellektual rivojlanishini ham ta'minlaydi va kelajakdagi o'qish va ijtimoiy hayotga tayyorgarlikni mustahkamlaydi.

Tarbiyachi o'yin jarayonini boshqaruvchi, yo'naltiruvchi va rag'batlantiruvchi shaxs sifatida muhim o'rin tutadi, bolaning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda interaktiv va zamonaviy o'yin texnologiyalarini tatbiq etadi va bolalarning hissiy, ijtimoiy va nutqiy rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi. Shu tariqa, o'yin texnologiyalari bolalarda nafaqat nutqiy kompetensiyani, balki mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni ham rivojlantiradi, bolaning o'z fikriga ishonchini oshiradi, yangilik yaratish istagini rag'batlantiradi va uning keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi uchun mustahkam poydevor yaratadi.

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МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЕТЯМ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные подходы и принципы методики преподавания русского языка детям. Особое внимание уделяется роли учителя, индивидуализации обучения и использованию игровых и мультимедийных технологий. Подчеркивается значение формирования интереса к языку как ключевого фактора успешного обучения.

Ключевые слова: русский язык, методика преподавания, дети, игровые технологии, индивидуальный подход.

Annotation: The article examines modern approaches and principles of teaching methodology for the Russian language to children. Special attention is paid to the teacher's role, the individualization of instruction, and the use of game-based and multimedia technologies. The importance of fostering interest in the language as a key factor for successful learning is emphasized.

Keywords: Russian language, teaching methodology, children, game-based technologies, individual approach.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada bolalarga rus tilini o'qitish metodikasining zamonaviy yondashuvlari va tamoyillari tahlil qilinadi. Unda o'qituvchining roli, ta'limni individuallashtirish hamda o'yin va multimediya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Tilda o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishni muvaffaqiyatli ta'limning asosiy omili sifatida shakllantirish muhimligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: rus tili, o'qitish metodikasi, bolalar, o'yin texnologiyalari, individual yondashuv.

Методика преподавания русского языка детям играет важную роль в формировании грамотной, культурной и творческой личности. Русский язык является не только средством общения, но и инструментом познания окружающего мира, а также основой для изучения других предметов (Иванова, 2021). Поэтому важно развивать у детей интерес к языку с самого раннего возраста. Современные педагогические подходы направлены на то, чтобы процесс обучения был доступным, занимательным и соответствовал возрастным особенностям учащихся.

Индивидуальный подход предполагает учет темпа развития, уровня восприятия и интересов каждого ребёнка. Педагог должен адаптировать методы и формы обучения под индивидуальные особенности учащихся (Петрова, 2020).

Наглядность является важным условием успешного усвоения знаний. Использование визуальных материалов картинок, карточек, схем, презентаций способствует лучшему пониманию и запоминанию новых слов и грамматических правил.

Игровая форма обучения особенно эффективна для младших школьников. Игровые методы, такие как языковые игры, песни, стихи, инсценировки, активизируют познавательную деятельность и делают процесс обучения увлекательным.

Постепенность и систематичность обучения обеспечивают прочное усвоение знаний. Переход от простого к сложному помогает детям логично выстраивать представления о языке и применять полученные знания на практике.

Развитие всех видов речевой деятельности чтения, письма, аудирования и говорения способствует формированию целостной языковой компетенции (Сидорова, 2019). Важно, чтобы ребёнок не только понимал язык, но и умел активно использовать его в общении.

Современная методика преподавания русского языка детям включает различные подходы, направленные на активизацию познавательной и речевой деятельности учащихся. Объяснительно-иллюстративный метод используется для введения новых понятий и правил с опорой на примеры. Репродуктивный метод помогает закрепить материал через упражнения и повторение. Проблемно-поисковый метод развивает мышление ребёнка и побуждает его к самостоятельному поиску решений. Игровые технологии делают процесс обучения эмоционально привлекательным и способствуют развитию творческих способностей. Важное значение имеет использование мультимедийных средств презентаций, видеоматериалов, интерактивных заданий, которые повышают мотивацию и вовлеченность учеников.

Учитель является центральной фигурой учебного процесса. Он не только передаёт знания, но и создаёт атмосферу доверия, поддержки и сотрудничества (Кузнецова, 2022). Эффективный педагог умеет мотивировать детей, поощрять их успехи и помогать преодолевать трудности. Терпение, внимание и доброжелательность основные качества, необходимые для успешной работы с младшими школьниками. Для формирования устойчивого интереса к русскому языку необходимо делать уроки разнообразными, эмоционально насыщенными и творческими.

Методика преподавания русского языка детям должна основываться на уважении к личности ребёнка и любви к языку. Главная цель обучения развитие интереса к русскому языку, формирование коммуникативных навыков и логического мышления. Добросердечная атмосфера, творческий подход и последовательность в обучении позволяют достичь высоких результатов и воспитать у детей любовь к родному слову.

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INSON HAYOTINI BOYITISHDA BAG‘RIKENGLIKNING O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tolerantlik haqida tushuncha, tolerantlikning internatsionalizm bilan bog‘likligi va bag‘rikenglikni bola tarbiysidan boshlash kerakligi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bag‘rikenglik tarbiyasi, sabr-toqatlilik, tolerantlik paradoksi, qadriyatlar, bag‘rikenglik deklaratsiyasi, tolerantlik tamoyillari, demokratik pozitsiyala, tolerantlik, internatsionalizm.

Tolerantlik – o‘zgalarning turmush tarzi, xulq-atvori, odatlari, his-tuyg‘ulari, fikr-mulohazalari, g‘oyalari va e’tiqodlariga nisbatan toqatli bo‘lish [8]. Tolerantlikning ildizlari qadimgi falsafiy oqimlardan boshlanadi. Masalan, Yunon faylasuflari tenglik va adolat haqida ko‘p yozgan. Bu g‘oyalar keyinchalik Yevropa ma’rifat-parvarlik davrida rivojlangan. Tolerantlik har bir insonning shaxsiy erkinligini hurmat qilishga asoslanadi. Bu jamiyatda tinchlik va barqarorlikni ta’minlash uchun muhimdir. Falsafiy nuqtai nazardan, u o‘zaro tushunish va hurmatga asoslanadi.

Bugungi kunda tolerantlik inson huquqlari va tenglik tamoyillari bilan chambarchas bog‘liq. Bu tamoyillar BMTning Umumjahon inson huquqlari deklaratsiyasida ham o‘z aksini topgan. Tolerantlik falsafasi global muammolarni hal qilishda asosiy rol o‘ynaydi [9].

O‘zbekiston kabi ko‘pmillatli davlatda tolerantlik alohida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turli xil dinlar va madaniyatlar bir joyda uyg‘un yashaydi. Tolerantlik bu uyg‘unlikni ta’minlashning asosiy omilidir.

Bag‘rikenglikni insonning boshqa odamlarga bo‘lgan munosabatining ko‘rinishlaridan biri sifatida anglash, tarbiya bu munosabatni salbiy bo‘lsa ham o‘zgar-tirmasligi mumkin: bizning bolani o‘z qarashlarini o‘zgartirishga, fikrlashga majburlashga haqqimiz yo‘q. Gap shundaki, u ilgari tanimagan narsani tan olishi, ilgari sevmagan narsasini sevib qolishini tan olishi mumkin. U ham o‘z munosabatiga ega. Bunda gap boshqacha va murakkabroq – bag‘rikenglik o‘z subyekti va obyektini birgalikda yashash holati bilan ta’minlashi mumkin va kerak; bag‘ri-kenglik tarbiyasi bolaga ushbu vaziyatga adekvat yordam berish uchun mo‘ljallangan. [3; 108–111]

Bag‘rikenglik, yuqorida qayd etkanimizdek, birinchi navbatda, sabr-toqatlilikni anglatadi. Shaxsiy imtiyozlardan qat’i nazar, boshqalarning qarashlariga, qiziqishlariga bag‘rikeng bo‘lishdir. Terminologiyaga murojaat qiladigan bo‘lsak, “bag‘rikenglik” so‘zi lotinchadan olingan bo‘lib, “tolerantia”, ya’ni “sabr-toqat” ma’nosini anglatadi [11] va insonlarning o‘zaro munosabatlarida muhim rol o‘ynab, boshqalar bilan fikr almashish, murosaga erishish va tinchlikni saqlashda asosiy omil sifatida ko‘riladi [10].

Tolerantlikning asosi va uning dinamikasining mumkin bo‘lgan maydoni, birinchi navbatda, shaxsning tajribasida yotadi va ishlaydi. Demak, bag‘rikenglik tarbiyasi – bu pedagogik nuqtai nazardan, bag‘rikenglikning ijobiy tajribasini maqsadli tashkil etish, ya’ni

boshqalarning nazarida ular qanday bo'lishidan qat'i nazar, ular bilan o'zaro munosabatni talab qiladigan shart-sharoitlarni maqsadli ravishda yaratishdir.

Zamonaviy dunyo o'zini namoyon qilish uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlarni taqdim etsada, uning shaxsiyatini namoyon etishga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lish muammosi ochiqlicha qolmoqda. Shuni aytib o'tish joyizki, haddan tashqari bag'rikenglik – tolerantlik paradoksi deb ataladigan narsaga olib kelishi mumkin. Bu shuni anglatadiki, haddan tashqari bag'rikenglik uning butunlay yo'q bo'lib ketishiga olib kelishi mumkin, chunki murosasizlikka nisbatan bag'rikenglik munosabati ikkinchisining tarqalishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun, bag'rikeng jamiyat murosasizlikka toqat qilmasligi kerak. Ushbu paradoks 1945-yilda Karl Popper tomonidan bildirilgan [6]. Bundan tashqari, haddan tashqari bag'rikenglik bolalarga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkin: ruxsat berish, har qanday noto'g'ri xatti-harakatlarning kechirilishi bolada tegishli munosabatni shakllantiradi. Qiyinchilik-lardan qochish va erkalash ularni hal qilishdan ko'ra ko'proq muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi, shuning uchun hayotning boshqalarga nisbatan bag'rikenglik munosabati, vaziyatni aniq ko'rish, shuningdek, nima foyda va nima zarar keltirishini tushunish kabi jihatlari nihoyatda muhimdir. Shuni esda tutish kerakki, hamma narsa me'yorida yaxshi [7].

Amaliyotsiz nazariya ko'p natija bermasligini hammamiz bilamiz. Qanday qilib o'zingizni axloqiy jihatdan tarbiyalash va atrofingizga ham toqat qilishingiz kerak? Avvalo, dunyodagi biron bir odam kimningdir qarashlari va manfaatlariga mos kelmasligi kerakligini qabul qilish kerak. Odamlar boshqalardan terining rangi, musiqiy didi va boshqalari bo'ladi, ammo bu ularni umuman yomonlashtirmaydi. O'rnatilgan va shakllangan dunyoqarashga ega bo'lgan kattalar uchun boshqalarga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirish bola yoki o'spiringa qaraganda qiyinroq. Har qanday uy poydevordan boshlanganidek, tarbiya ham bolalikdan boshlanadi. Boshqalarga hurmat tuyg'ularini uyg'otish, ularning shaxsiy hayotiga bo'lgan huquqlarini tan olish bolalik davrida o'rnatilishi kerak. Bundan tashqari, bunga nafaqat ot-onalar, balki oiladan tashqarida o'quvchi uchun murabbiy bo'lgan o'qituvchi ham jalb qilinishi kerak.

Shunday qilib, bag'rikenglik – bu har bir inson individual va shaxsiy mustaqil hayot kechirish huquqiga ega ekanligini aniq tushunishga asoslangan boshqa odamlarning qadriyatlariga nisbatan bag'rikeng, hurmatli munosabatdir.

Yuqorida aytib o'tkanimizdek, lotinchda tolerantlik atamasi sabr-toqatni anglatadi dedik, ammo bu tushunchaning ma'nosi ancha kengroq. 185 mamlakat tomonidan qabul qilingan YUNESKONing bag'rikenglik deklaratsiyasida [1] ushbu tushuncha turli millat, madaniyat, din vakillari huquqlarini hurmat qilish, insonning individualligini namoyon etish va ifoda etish shakllari va usullarini ularning xilma-xilligida qabul qilish sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Bag'rikenglik zamonaviy ko'p o'lchovli dunyoda hayot normasi bo'lib, shaxs va jamiyatning barqarorligini belgilaydi. Tolerantlik tamoyillarining buzilishi mojarolar, urushlar, sivilizatsiya-ning yo'q qilinishiga olib keladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, bu nafaqat etnik, madaniy, diniy yoki boshqa xususiyatlarga ko'ra bizdan farq qiladigan odamga toqat qilish, balki uning shaxsiyatining o'ziga xosligini tan olish qobiliyatidir.

Shu bilan bir qatorda, bag'rikenglik – bu bir-biriga o'xshamaydigan odamlar bilan o'zaro tushunish san'ati. Tushunish, boshqasining pozitsiyasini egallash qobiliyati odamni bag'rikeng qiladi. Odamlar va odamlar bilan munosabatlar inson hayotining mohiyatidir. Ushbu munosabatlar orqali biz dunyoni va o'zimizni bilib olamiz, ular bizning shaxsiyatimizni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Bag'rikenglik boshqalar bilan yashash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi, shoshilinch hukm chiqarmasdan, subyektiv baho bermasdan ularning boshqacha bo'lish huquqini qabul qiladi. Bag'rikeng odam o'zini boshqarish qobiliyatiga ega, stereotiplardan qochadi, turli xil qarashlar va fikrlarni tan oladi, demokratik

pozitsiyalarda turadi. Ushbu sifatdan mahrum bo'lgan odam, qoida tariqasida, boshqalarni qoralashga va rad etishga moyil bo'lib, o'z kamchiliklarini sezmaydi, dunyodagi hamma narsani qora va oqqa, odamlarni yaxshi va yomonga ajratadi, avtoritarizmga intiladi.

Tolerantlik internatsionalizm tushunchasi bilan ham chambarchash bog'liqdir. Internatsionalizm, ya'ni baynalmilalchilik (*lotincha inter – aro, natio – xalq*) – turli millat, irqdagi kishilarning xalqaro birdamligini ifoda etadigan tushuncha. Internatsionalizm tarixiy taraqqiyotning ma'lum bosqichida, millatlarning kelib chiqishi va millatlararo munosabatlar natijasida muomalaga kiritilgan tushunchadir. Internatsionalizmning tub mohiyatini insonparvarlik, tolerantlik g'oyalari, xalqaro hamdo'stlik, birdamlik, hamjihatlik kabi umuminsoniy tamoyillar tashkil qiladi. Internatsionalizmni burjua davlatlarining kelib chiqishi bilan bog'liq holda izohlash masalaga noto'g'ri yondashish demakdir. Tarix saboqlariga ko'ra, xalqaro ham-do'stlik va hamkorlik tamoyillari jahon xalqlarining turmush tarzida hamisha mavjud bo'lgan. Internatsionalizm g'oyasi Aflotun, Arastu, Forobiy, Ibn Sino, Nizomiy, Navoiy, Abay va boshqa allomalarning asarlarida atroflicha bayon etilgan. Internatsionalizm tushunchasini sinfiy, siyosiy va mafkuraviy jihatdan ta'riflash uning umuminsoniy mohiyatini soxtalashtirishga sabab bo'ladi. Internatsionalizm g'oyalari va tamoyillarining uzluksiz rivojlanib borishi umuminsoniy demokratik qadriyatlar ta'sirining kuchayishi, jahonda xalqaro tolerantlikning barqarorligi bilan bog'liqdir. Bugungi kunda yurtimizda 130 dan ziyod millat va elat vakillarining o'zaro ahil, tinch-totuv yashab kelayotgani, Vatan va mamlakatning gullab-yashnashi uchun bir yoqadan bosh chiqarib mehnat qilayotgani internat-sionalizmning amaldagi haqiqiy ifodasidir [5].

Demak, bag'rikenglik inson hayotini boyitadi, chunki boshqa odamlarga samimiy qiziqish, ularni tushunish istagi dunyoqarashni kengaytiradi, dunyoni barcha ko'rinishlarida bilish istagini rivojlantiradi, bebaho hayotiy tajribani to'playdi.

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MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIK G‘OYASI – UMUMBASHARIY QADRIYAT

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada turli etnik madaniyat vakillari o‘rtasidagi ziddiyatlarning oldini olish bo‘yicha faoliyatning eng istiqbolli yo‘nalishlaridan biri bu yosh avlodning tashqi dunyoga nisbatan bag‘rikeng munosabatini maqsadli shakllantirishdir. Bu borada ta’lim tizimi, shubhasiz, alohida rol o‘ynayshi to‘g‘risida so‘z boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ijtimoiy instituti, ijtimoiy tuzilmalar, xulq-atvor normalari, qadriyat belgilari, bag‘rikenglik munosabat, tolerantlik, pedagogika, konsepsiya, bag‘rikenglik tamoyillari.

Yangi O‘zbekiston bugun butun dunyo mamlakatlari uchun bag‘rikenglik namunalarini o‘zida mujassam etgan davlat sifatida namuna bo‘lmoqda. O‘zbek millatiga xos bag‘rikenglik xususiyatlari barcha mamlakatlar uchun andoza bo‘lib xizmat qiladi, deb ayta olamiz. Zamonaviy xalqaro munosabatlar sharoitida davlatlararo miqyosda bag‘rikenglikni saqlash va mustahkamlash, nafaqat ayrim mamlakatlarning orzu-intilishlariga, balki o‘zaro hamkorlik aloqalariga ham bog‘liqdir [2].

Bugun yurtimizda turli din va millat vakillari emin-erkin yashab kelmoqda. Bu esa fuqarolarning vijdon erkinligi ularning millati, irqi va dinidan qat’iy nazar to‘liq kafolatlangan hamda bag‘rikenglik g‘oyalari huquqiy jihatdan ta’minlan-ganini ko‘rsatadi. Shu jihatdan, turli millat va din vakillari o‘rtasida hamjihatlikni mustahkamlash, bag‘rikenglik g‘oyalarini qaror toptirish borasida keng qamrovli va izchil siyosat amalga oshirilmoqda.

Bag‘rikenglik – insonlarning bir-biriga nisbatan hurmat, sabr-toqat va tushunish hissi bilan yondashish. Bu tushuncha, asosan, jamiyatda tinchlikni saqlash, ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta’minlash va insonlar o‘rtasida do‘stlikni rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bag‘rikenglik, avvalo, turli xil fikrlar, e‘tiqodlar va hayot tarzlariga nisbatan ochiqlikni anglatadi. Har bir insonning o‘ziga xos fikrlash tarziga ega ekanligini tan olish, ularni hurmat qilish va ularning farqliligini qabul qilish bag‘rikenglikning asosiy tamoyillaridan biridir. Bu, o‘z navbatida, ijtimoiy muhitda ziddiyatlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi [1].

Bag‘rikenglik insoniyat tomonidan erishilgan eng katta yutuqlardan biridir, bundan keyingi taraqqiyot uchun ham u muhim omillardan bo‘lib qolaveradi. Qolaversa, bag‘rikenglik o‘zbek xalqi ma’naviyati va madaniyatining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Odamlarni halollik va poklik, mehr-shafqat, birodarlik va bag‘rikenglikka da’vat etadi. Bag‘rikenglik eng go‘zal insoniy fazilatlardan bo‘lib, biror-bir millat yoki dinga mansubligidan qat’iy nazar barchaga birdek yaxshi munosabatda bo‘lish, muhtojlarga yordam qo‘lini cho‘zish, ezgu maqsad yo‘lida birlashish kabi yuksak axloqlarning yuzaga chiqishida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Millatlararo totuvlik g‘oyasi – umumbashariy qadriyat bo‘lib, turli xil xalqlar birgalikda istiqomat qiladigan mintaq va davlatlar milliy taraqqiyotini belgilaydi, shu joydagi tinchlik va barqarorlikning kafolati bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, jamiyatda tinchlik va barqarorlikning kafolati bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Yurtimizda nafaqat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, siyosiy sohalar, balki zaminimizda istiqomat qilib kelayotgan turli millat va elatlar o‘rtasida do‘stlik rishtalarini yanada mustahkamlash, diniy bag‘rikenglik

tamoyillarini qaror toptirishga ham alohida e'tibor qaratib kelinadi. Har bir millatning umumiy manfaatlari bilan birga o'z qadriyatlari ham bor. O'zbekiston kabi ko'pmillatli mamlakatda turli millatlar manfaatlarini uyg'unlashtirish, ular orasida totuvlikni ta'minlash taraqqiyotning hal qiluvchi omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun ham mamlakatimizda bu masalaga katta e'tibor berib kelinmoqda [3]. Madaniy xilma-xillik va bag'rikenglik madaniyatining ahamiyati g'oyalari-ning mantiqiy rivojlanishi YUNESKONing Parijdagi bosh konferensiyasining 31-sessiyasining qarorlari edi (2001), unda "madaniy xilma-xillikka hurmat, bag'rikenglik, muloqot va ishonch va o'zaro tushunish sharoitida hamkorlik, tinchlik va xalqaro xavfsizlikning eng yaxshi kafolatlari" [4].

«Tolerant» atamasining lug'aviy ma'nosi lotincha «tole gage» (chidamoq) so'zidan olingan. Tolerantlik biror narsani, o'zgacha fikr yoki qarashni, o'z shaxsiy tushunchalaridan qat'i nazar, imkon qadar bag'rikenglik va chidam bilan qabul qilishni anglatadi. Diniy bag'rikenglik vijdon erkinligi va ma'naviyat jihatdan katta ahamiyat kasb etadi, u boshqa shaxs yo dinga hurmatni bildiradi. Turli din hamda konfessiya vakillari e'tiqodida aqidaviy farqlar bo'lishiga qaramay, ularning yonma-yon va o'zaro tinch-totuv yashashini anglatadi [6].

Shunday qilib, ma'lum darajada xalqaro hujjatlar madaniy xilma-xillikning ahamiyati va madaniyatlarning teng muloqoti haqidagi g'oyalar bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lgan "bag'rikenglik" tushunchasining izchil mazmunini taqdim etdi. Bundan tashqari, bag'rikenglik erkinlik va shaxsiy huquqlar qadriyatlarini tan olishga asoslangan dunyoga faol munosabat fenomeni ekanligi ta'kidlandi. Shu bilan birga, bag'rikenglikning o'z chegaralari borligi va ularni ruhoniylar va ahmoqlar deb hisoblash mumkin emasligi aytilgan.

Shu bilan birga, ilmiy foydalanishda "tolerantlik" atamasini ko'pincha ilmiy adabiyotlarda sinonim sifatida ishlatiladigan "bag'rikenglik" atamasi bilan almashtirish to'g'risida tabiiy savol tug'ilishi mumkin. Buning uchun lug'atlar va ilmiy adabiyotlarda ushbu ta'riflarning talqinlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilamiz. S.I.Ochegovning "Rus tilining izohli lug'atida" tushuntirishlardan biri sifatida quyidagilar taklif qilingan: "tolerant – bu boshqalarning fikri, munosabati va xatti-harakatlariga dushmanliksiz sabr-toqat bilan munosabatda bo'lishni biladigan kishi" [9; 944]. I.Kona tomonidan tahrirlangan "Etika lug'ati" "tolerantlik" atamasining quyidagi tushunchasini shakllantiradi: bu – "boshqa odamlarning manfaatlarini, e'tiqodlari, ishonchlari va xulq-atvor odatlariga munosabatni tavsiflovchi axloqiy xususiyatdir. [7; 432] "Siyosatshunoslik"da bag'rikenglik fenomeni boshqa nuqtai nazardan qaraladi va, avvalambor, "boshqalarning e'tiqodlari, pozitsiyalari yoki harakatlarini xohlash, hatto yoqtirmaslikka qaramaslik" [10]. Uning ta'rifni tushunishi psixologiya va pedagogikaning ensiklopedik lug'atida keltirilgan: "Tolerantlik – bag'rikenglik – bu shaxsiy xususiyat, tinchlanish va har qanday narsaga toqat qilish qobiliyati (masalan, boshqalarning fikri)", bu "nizolarning oldini olishga yordam beradi" [10]. Shu bilan birga, bag'rikenglik faqat shaxsiy munosabatlar bilan cheklanmaydi. U ijtimoiy va siyosiy hayotda ham o'z aksini topadi. Bag'rikeng siyosat, jamiyatdagi turli guruhlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni yaxshilashga, fuqarolar o'rtasida tinchlikni saqlashga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, bag'rikenglik – bu insoniyatning eng muhim qadriyatlaridan biridir. U nafaqat shaxsiy munosabatlarda, balki ijtimoiy hayotda ham tinchlik va barqarorlikni ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Har birimiz bag'rikenglikni rivojlantirishga hissa qo'shishimiz kerak, chunki bu nafaqat bizning shaxsiy hayotimizni, balki butun jamiyatimizni yaxshilashga olib keladi.

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YOSH AVLODNI TARBIYALASHDA TOLERANTLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tolerantlik tushunchasi haqida nazariy fikrlar va yosh avlodni tarbiyalashda tolerantlik madaniyatini shakllantirish borasida so‘z boradi. Yyuksak ma‘naviyatli, mustaqil fikrlaydigan, zamonaviy bilim va kasb-hunarni puxta egallagan yoshlarni tarbiyalash, ularda milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga hurmat hissini yuksaltirish, o‘g‘il-qizlar qalbi va ongida mafkuraviy immunitet shakllantirishdan iborat ekanligi haqida fikrlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: taraqqiyot, ravnaq, mintaqah, globallashuv, bag‘rikenglik tamoyili, farovon hayot, deklarasiya, madaniyat, diniy e‘tiqod, dinlararo hamjihatlik, umuminsoniy qadriyat.

Globalashuv jarayoni hayotimizga tobora tez va chuqur kirib kelayotganining asosiy omili va sababi xususida gapirganda shuni obyektiv tan olish kerakki, bugungi kunda har qaysi davlatning taraqqiyoti va ravnaqi nafaqat yaqin hamda uzoq qo‘shnilar, balki jahon miqyosida boshqa mintaqah va hududlar bilan shunday chambarchas bog‘lanib boryaptiki, biron mamlakatning bu jarayondan chetda turishi ijobiy natijalarga olib kelmasligini tushunish, anglash qiyin emasdir. Dunyoda globallashuv jarayoni shiddatli tus olgan bugungi kunda turli madaniyat va dinga mansub xalqlar o‘rtasida o‘zaro muloqot va hamkorlikni

rivojlantirish dolzarb ahamiyatga ega [7; 167-173]. Zero, bugun yakka shaxs yoki alohida millat va davlatning o'z qobig'idan chiqmasdan taraqqiy etishi tasavvurga sig'maydi. Bunda esa, avvalo, bag'rikenglik tamoyili ustuvor bo'lmog'i zarur. O'z navbatida, mazkur tamoyilning qaror topishi har qanday davlatning tinch, osoyishta va farovon hayotiga ham kafolatdir.

YUNESKO ustavida ta'kidlanganidek, o'zaro bir-birini tushunmaslik butun insoniyat tarixi davomida o'zaro shubhalanish va ishonchsizlikning ildiz otishiga sababi bo'lgan, bu esa oqibatda turli ixtiloflar va nizolarga olib kelgan. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, buyuk ajdodimiz Abu Rayhon Beruniyning "Odamlar bilmagan narsalariga dushmanlik ko'zi bilan qaraydilar" degan, qozq xalqining "Yuzi boshqa – yuragi bir, tili boshqa – tilagi bir" degan naql so'zlarida hamda qozoq xalqining ulug' mutafarrik shoiri Abay Qunonboyevning "Odamzotni suyushning ikki sharti bor: biri – "bavurim (jigarim)" deb, ikkinchisi – "Haq yo'li shu deb" [8] singari fikrlari chuqur mazmunga egaligini qayd etish lozim. Bag'rikenglik – boshqa fikr va qarashga toqatli bo'lish, o'ziga ma'qul va maqbul bo'lmagan e'tiqod va ibodatlarni cheklemaslik, qoralamaslik kabilarda namoyan bo'ladi.

Bag'rikenglik bir-birini anglash, tushunish va qabul qilish demakdir. Yer yuzidagi turfa madaniyatga hurmat bilan yondashishga ham shu ta'rif beriladi. Bilim, samimiyat, vijdon va e'tiqod uyg'unligi natijasida yuzaga keladigan bu tushuncha faqat ma'naviy burchgina emas, balki siyosiy, huquqiy ehtiyoj ham sanaladi. Eng asosiysi, bag'rikenglik tufayli tinchlik ta'minlanadi, turli nizo, urushlar kelib chiqishining oldi olinadi.

Diyorimizda fuqarolar totuvligi, barqarorligi, turli millat vakillari tinchligi va hamjihatligini ta'minlash, vatandoshlarimiz ongida ko'pmillatli yagona oila tuyg'usini mustahkamlash, milliy madaniy markazlar, do'stlik jamiyatlari faoliyatini har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash va rivojlantirish, xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan madaniy-ma'rifiy aloqalarni kengaytirish borasida ko'plab samarali ishlar olib borilmoqda [3].

Ko'pmillatli respublikamizda o'zbeklar asosiy etnik guruhni tashkil qiladi. Shu bilan birga rus, qoraqalpoq, tatar, qozoq, tojik kabi ko'plab millat vakillar ham yashaydi. Ularning hammasi Konstitutsiyada kafolatlangan teng huquqlardan foydalanadi. Qomusimizning 19-moddasida O'zbekiston Respublikasida barcha fuqarolar bir xil huquq va erkinlikka egaligi, jinsi, irqi, millati, tili, dini, ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi, e'tiqodi, shaxsi va ijtimoiy mavqeidan qat'i nazar, qonun oldida tengligi belgilab qo'yilgan.

Ta'kidlash joizki, O'zbekistonda ta'lim islohoti orqali o'quv jarayonida millatlararo hamjihatlik, e'tiqod va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi hurmatga asoslangan tarbiya berishga alohida ahamiyat beriladi. Shuningdek, davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblangan yoshlarni har tomonlama barkamol qilib tarbiyalash, millatlarning tili, madaniyati, urf-odatini asrab-avaylash, yuksak ma'naviyatli, mustaqil fikrlaydigan, zamonaviy bilim va kasb-hunarni puxta egallagan yoshlarni tarbiyalash, ularda milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga hurmat hissini yuksaltirish, o'g'il-qizlar qalbi va ongida mafkuraviy immunitet shakllantirishdan iborat.

O'zbekistonda etnik va milliy kamsitishga qarshi qonunchilik bazasi mavjud. Milliy va etnik kamsitishga yo'l qo'ymaslik, qonun asosida shunday holatlarga qarshi kurashish uchun alohida mexanizm ishlab chiqilgan. Shunga qaramay, ijtimoiy adolat va bag'rikenglikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan qonun amaliyotini yanada mustahkamlash talab etiladi.

Jamiyatdagi bag'rikenglikni saqlashda oilaning ham roli katta. Oila mustahkamligi, xonadondagi to'g'ri tarbiya jamiyatning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, milliy xavfsizligi, ravnaqi, taraqqiyotini belgilovchi hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. Bu yoshlar o'rtasidagi hurmat va qadr-qimmat, turli millatlarning o'zaro munosabatlariga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Shuningdek, yoshlarda bag'rikenglik madaniyatini shakllantirish orqali davlatni mustahkamlash, xavfsizlikni muhofaza qilish, ularda jamiyat tinchligi va farovonligini ta'minlash mas'uliyatini kuchaytirish, ayniqsa o'g'il-qizlarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida hayotga tayyorlash mumkin.

Ma'lumki, bag'rikenglik g'oyasi – turli millat va elatlar vakillarining bir zamin, bir vatanda olijanob g'oya va niyatlar yo'lida hamkor hamda hamjihat bo'lib yashashini anglatadi. Qadim-qadimdan milliy qadriyatlarimiz ezgulik g'oyalariga asoslanib, yaxshilik, tinchlik, do'stlik kabi fazilatlarga tayanib kelgan. Odamlarni halollik, poklik, mehr-oqibat va bag'rikenglikka chorlagan.

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BAG'RIKENGLIK – ODAMLARNING QADRIYATLARIGA NISBATAN HURMATLI MUNOSABAT

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Annotatsiya. Bag'rikenglik – bu bir-biriga o'xshamaydigan odamlarning oz'aro tushunish san'ati ekanligi, bag'rikenglik insoniy munosabatlarning muhim xususiyat ifodasi sifatida kishilar o'rtasidagi do'stlik, mehr-muhabbat, o'zaro yordam, hamkorlik, hamjihatlik, hamdardlik, tinchlik, osoyishtalik kabi munosabatlarni aks ettirishi haqida hamda bag'rikenglik tarbiyaning bolalikdan boshlanishi borasida fikrlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlari: bag'rikenglik, tolerantlik, tolerantlik paradoksi, mantiqiy paradoks, murosasizlik, bag'rikenglik munosabat, qadriyat, barqarorlik, tolerantlik tamoyillari, insoniy munosabatlam.

Bag'rikenglik, birinchi navbatda, sabr-toqatlilikdir. Shaxsiy imtiyozlardan qat'i nazar, boshqalarning qarashlariga, qiziqishlariga bag'rikenglikdir. Terminolo-giya bo'yicha gapiradigan bo'lsak, "bag'rikenglik" so'zi lotincha "tolerantia"dan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, "chidamlilik", "sabrlik", "bardoshlik", "toqatlilik" degan ma'nonilarni anglatadi [2; 80–83]. Bag'rikenglik tamoyili aqidabozlikdan, haqiqatni mutlaklashtirishdan voz kechishni anglatadi va inson huquqlari sohasidagi xalqaro huquqiy hujjatlarda belgilangan qoidalarni tasdiqlaydi. Bu tamoyilga ko'ra, har kim o'z e'tiqodiga amal qilishda erkindir va har kim bu

huquqqa boshqalar ham ega ekanligini tan olmog'i lozim. Bir kishining qarashlari boshqalarga majburan singdirilishi mumkin emas. Tolerantlikni alohida shaxslar, guruhlar va davlatlar namoyon qilishi lozim [9].

Zamonaviy dunyo o'zini namoyon qilish uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlarni taqdim etsada, uning shaxsiyatini namoyon etishga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lish muammosi ochiqlicha qolmoqda. Kiyim-kechak, musiqa, sport – har kim dunyo haqidagi tasavvuriga qarab o'z qiziqish doirasini tanlaydi, ammo afsuski, ko'p odamlar buni tushunmaydilar yoki tushunishni xohlamaydilar. O'zlariga nisbatan salbiy munosabat tufayli odamlar o'zlarini biron bir narsada kamsitilgan deb bilishadi. Shuning uchun ular jamiyatdagi bag'rikenglikni chaqirishadi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bu haqda nafaqat zulm qilganlar, balki barcha odamlar ham bilishlari kerak.

Chunonchi, bu yerda ham tanganing ikki tomoni bor: tolerantlik paradoksi yoki tolerantlik chegarasini belgilash paradoksi. Bu Karl Popper tomonidan 1945-yilda "Ochiq jamiyat va uning dushmanlari" asarida bildirilgan hamda cheksiz bag'rikenglik tolerantlikning yo'q bo'lib ketishiga olib keladi, deb ta'kidlagan qarorlar nazariyasidagi mantiqiy paradoks, chunki murosasizlikka bag'rikenglik ikkinchisining keng tarqalishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun bag'rikenglikni saqlash murosasizlarga nisbatan murosasiz munosabatni talab qiladi, bu esa o'z navbatida murosasizlikni aniqlash chegaralarini xiralashtiradi [3]. Zo'ravonlikka yo'l qo'ymaslik to'g'risida shunga o'xshash paradoks mavjud bo'lib, unda zo'ravonlikning mutlaq taqiqlanishi zo'ravonlikni jilovlay olmasligiga olib keladi.

Tolerantlik paradoksidan xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, tolerantlik chegarasini chizish urinishlari mag'lubiyatga uchraydi, bu esa "o'z" va "notolerant" o'rtasidagi chegaraga olib keladi, ya'ni tolerantlik tushunchasiga mantiqiy paradoks kiritilgan. Uni bartaraf etish uchun bag'rikenglikni xulq-atvor normasi sifatida rad etadiganlarga nisbatan murosasizlik va ayrim hollarda bag'rikenglikni rad etadiganlarga nisbatan murosasizlik ajralib turishi kerak, umuman olganda, uni zarur deb biladi [3].

Bundan tashqari, haddan tashqari bag'rikenglik bolalarga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkin: ruxsat berish, har qanday noto'g'ri xatti-harakatlarning kechirilishi bolada tegishli munosabatni shakllantiradi. Qiyinchiliklardan qochish va erkalash ularni hal qilishdan ko'ra ko'proq muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi, shuning uchun hayotning boshqalarga nisbatan bag'rikenglik munosabati, vaziyatni aniq ko'rish, shuningdek, nima foyda va nima zarar keltirishini tushunish kabi jihatlari nihoyatda muhimdir. Shuni esda tutish kerakki, hamma narsa me'yorida yaxshi.

Amaliyotsiz nazariya ko'p natija bermasligini bilamiz. Qanday qilib o'zingizni axloqiy jihatdan tarbiyalashingiz kerak, balki atrofingizga ham toqat qilishingiz kerakdir? Avvalo, dunyodagi biron bir odam kimningdir qarashlari va manfaatlariga mos kelmasligini ham qabul qilish kerak. Odamlar boshqalardan terining rangi, musiqiy didi va hakazoalar bo'lishi mumkin, ammo bu ularni umuman yomonlashtirmaydi. O'rnatilgan va shakllangan dunyoqarashga ega bo'lgan kattalar uchun boshqalarga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirish bolaga yoki o'spiringa qaraganda qiyinroq. Har qanday uy poydevordan boshlanganidek, tarbiya ham bolalikdan boshlanadi. Boshqalarga hurmat tuyg'ularini uyg'otish, ularning shaxsiy hayotiga bo'lgan huquqlarini tan olish bolalik davrida o'rnatilishi kerak. Bundan tashqari, bunga nafaqat ota-onalar, balki oiladan tashqarida talaba-o'quvchi uchun murabbiy bo'lgan o'qituvchi ham jalb qilinishi kerak.

Shunday qilib, bag'rikenglik – bu har bir inson individual va shaxsiy mustaqil hayot kechirish huquqiga ega ekanligini aniq tushunishga asoslangan boshqa odamlarning qadriyatlariga nisbatan bag'rikeng, hurmatli munosabatdir. Albatta, siz bolaligingizdan bu

ustida ishlashingiz kerak, ammo bu yo‘qolgan darsni to‘ldirish mumkin emas degani emas – amaliyot va shu tarzda odam madaniyatga qo‘shilib, hayotda bunday munosabatni qo‘llashda yaxshiroq yordam berishini anglash.

Yuqorida aytganimizdek, tolerantlik atamasi sabr-toqatni anglatadi, ammo bu tushunchaning ma‘nosi ancha kengroq. 185 mamlakat tomonidan qabul qilingan YUNESKOning bag‘rikenglik Deklaratsiyasida [5] ushbu tushuncha turli millat, madaniyat, din vakillari huquqlarini hurmat qilish, insonning individualligini namoyon etish va ifoda etish shakllari hamda usullarini ularning xilma-xilligida qabul qilish sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Bag‘rikenglik zamonaviy keng o‘lchovli dunyoda hayot normasi hisoblanib, shaxs va jamiyatning barqarorligini belgilaydi. Tolerantlik tamoyillarining buzilishi mojarolar, urushlar, sivilizatsiyaning yo‘q qilinishiga olib keladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, bu nafaqat etnik, madaniy, diniy yoki boshqa xususiyatlarga ko‘ra bizdan farq qiladigan odamga toqat qilish, balki uning shaxsiyatining o‘ziga xosligi va o‘ziga xosligini tan olish qobiliyatidir.

Ba‘zida soxta bag‘rikenglik ikkiyuzlamachilik yoki befarqlikka yaqin bo‘ladi. Ular shunchaki yoqimsiz odamni sezmaslikka yoki undan qochishga harakat qilishadi. Bag‘rikenglikdan mahrum bo‘lgan odam tajovuzkor va ziddiyatli, u ijtimoiy jihatdan uzoqni ko‘ra olmaydi, faqat yaqindan ko‘ra oladigan narsalarni qabul qiladi. Bag‘rikenglik faol hayotiy pozitsiyani, ajralishni emas, balki munosabatlarda ishtirok etishni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Bag‘rikenglik – bu bir-biriga o‘xshamaydigan odamlarning oz‘aro tushunish san‘ati. Tushunish, boshqasining pozitsiyasini egallash qobiliyati odamni bag‘rikeng qiladi. Odamlarning bir-biri bilan munosabatlari inson hayotining mohiyatidir. Ushbu munosabatlar orqali biz dunyoni va o‘zimizni bilib olamiz, ular bizning shaxsiyatimizni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Bag‘rikenglik boshqalar bilan yashash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi, shoshilinch hukm chiqarmasdan, subyektiv baho bermasdan ularning boshqacha bo‘lish huquqini qabul qiladi. Bag‘rikeng odam o‘zini boshqarish qobiliyatiga ega, stereotiplardan qochadi, turli xil qarashlar va fikrlarni tan oladi, demokratik pozitsiyalarda turadi. Ushbu sifatdan mahrum bo‘lgan odam, qoida tariqasida, boshqalarni qoralashga va rad etishga moyil bo‘lib, o‘z kamchiliklarini sezmaydi, dunyodagi hamma narsani qora va oqga, odamlarni yaxshi va yomonga ajratadi, avtoritarizmga intiladi.

Bag‘rikenglik insoniy munosabatlarning muhim xususiyat ifodasi sifatida kishilar o‘rtasidagi do‘stlik, mehr-muhabbat, o‘zaro yordam, hamkorlik, hamjihatlik, hamdardlik, tinchlik, osoyishtalik kabi munosabatlarni aks ettiradi. Shunga ko‘ra fuqarolik jamiyati rivojlanishi natijasida bag‘rikenglik ham jamiyat taraqqiyoti bilan bog‘liq ravishda tobora rivojlanib, o‘zining mazmunini boyitib boradi. Yosh avlodni bag‘rikenglik ruhida va bag‘rikenglik tamoyillari asosida tarbiyalash orqali faol fuqarolik pozitsiyasiga ega, huquqiy va ma‘naviy barkamol avlodni tarbiyalashdek ustuvor vazifani bajarishga erishish hamda fuqarolik jamiyati shakllanish jarayonini yangi bosqichga olib chiqishda muhim qadam bo‘ladi [4; 453-463].

Bag‘rikenglik inson hayotini boyitadi, chunki boshqa odamlarga samimiy qiziqish, ularni tushunish istagi dunyoqarashni kengaytiradi, dunyoni barcha ko‘rinishlarida bilish istagini rivojlantiradi, bebaho hayotiy tajribani to‘playdi.

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TOLERANTLIK VA INTERNATSIONALIZM TUSHUNCHASI HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada tolerantlik haqida tushuncha, tolerantlikning internatsionalizm bilan bog'likligi va bag'rikenglikni bola tarbiysidan boshlash kerakligi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bag'rikenglik tarbiyasi, sabr-toqatlilik, tolerantlik paradoksi, qadriyatlar, bag'rikenglik deklaratsiyasi, tolerantlik tamoyillari, demokratik pozitsiyala, tolerantlik, internatsionalizm.

Bugungi kunda tolerantlik inson huquqlari va tenglik tamoyillari bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Bu tamoyillar BMTning Umumjahon inson huquqlari deklaratsiyasida ham o'z aksini topgan. Tolerantlik falsafasi global muammolarni hal qilishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi [9]. O'zbekiston kabi ko'pmillatli davlatda tolerantlik alohida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turli xil dinlar va madaniyatlar bir joyda uyg'un yashaydi. Tolerantlik bu uyg'unlikni ta'minlashning asosiy omilidir.

Tolerantlik jamiyatda turli xil e'tiqod, madaniyat va qarashlarga hurmat ko'rsatish va ularni qabul qilishni anglatadi. Bu so'z lotincha "tolerare" so'zidan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, "sabr qilish" yoki "bardosh berish" ma'nosini beradi [12].

Bag'rikenglikni insonning boshqa odamlarga bo'lgan munosabatining ko'rinishlaridan biri sifatida anglash, tarbiya bu munosabatni salbiy bo'lsa ham o'zgar-tirmasligi mumkin: bizning bolani o'z qarashlarini o'zgartirishga, fikrlashga majburlashga haqqimiz yo'q. Gap shundaki, u ilgari tanimagan narsani tan olishi, ilgari sevmagan narsasini sevib qolishini tan olishi mumkin. U ham o'z munosa-batiga ega. Bunda gap boshqacha va murakkabroq – bag'rikenglik o'z subyekti va obyektini birgalikda yashash holati bilan ta'minlashi mumkin va kerak; bag'ri-kenglik tarbiyasi bolaga ushbu vaziyatga adekvat yordam berish uchun mo'ljal-langan. [3; 108–111]

Bag'rikenglik, yuqorida qayd etkanimizdek, birinchi navbatda, sabr-toqatlilikni anglatadi. Shaxsiy imtiyozlardan qat'i nazar, boshqalarning qarashlariga, qiziqishlariga bag'rikeng bo'lishdir. Terminologiyaga murojaat qiladigan bo'lsak, "bag'rikenglik" so'zi lotinchadan olingan bo'lib, "tolerantia", ya'ni "sabr-toqat" ma'nosini anglatadi [11] va insonlarning o'zaro munosabatlarida muhim rol o'ynab, boshqalar bilan fikr almashish, murosaga erishish va tinchlikni saqlashda asosiy omil sifatida ko'riladi [10].

Tolerantlikning asosi va uning dinamikasining mumkin bo'lgan maydoni, birinchi navbatda, shaxsning tajribasida yotadi va ishlaydi. Demak, bag'rikenglik tarbiyasi – bu pedagogik nuqtai nazardan, bag'rikenglikning ijobiy tajribasini maqsadli tashkil etish, ya'ni boshqalarning nazarida ular qanday bo'lishidan qat'i nazar, ular bilan o'zaro munosabatni talab qiladigan shart-sharoitlarni maqsadli ravishda yaratishdir.

Bag'rikenglik – bu har bir inson individual va shaxsiy mustaqil hayot kechirish huquqiga ega ekanligini aniq tushunishga asoslangan boshqa odamlarning qadriyatlariga nisbatan bag'rikeng, hurmatli munosabatdir.

Tolerantlik internatsionalizm tushunchasi bilan ham chambarchash bog'liqdir. Internatsionalizm, ya'ni baynalmilalchilik (*lotincha inter – aro, natio – xalq*) – turli millat, irqdagi kishilarning xalqaro birdamligini ifoda etadigan tushuncha. Internatsionalizm tarixiy taraqqiyotning ma'lum bosqichida, millatlarning kelib chiqishi va millatlararo munosabatlar natijasida muomalaga kiritilgan tushunchadir. Internatsionalizmning tub mohiyatini insonparvarlik, tolerantlik g'oyalari, xalqaro hamdo'stlik, birdamlik, hamjihatlik kabi umuminsoniy tamoyillar tashkil qiladi. Internatsionalizmni burjua davlatlarining kelib chiqishi bilan bog'liq holda izohlash masalaga noto'g'ri yondashish demakdir. Tarix saboqlariga ko'ra, xalqaro ham-do'stlik va hamkorlik tamoyillari jahon xalqlarining turmush tarzida hamisha mavjud bo'lgan. Internatsionalizm g'oyasi Aflotun, Arastu, Forobiy, Ibn Sino, Nizomiy, Navoiy, Abay va boshqa allomalarning asarlarida atroflicha bayon etilgan. Internatsionalizm tushunchasini sinfiy, siyosiy va mafkuraviy jihatdan ta'riflash uning umuminsoniy mohiyatini soxtalashtirishga sabab bo'ladi. Internatsionalizm g'oyalari va tamoyillarining uzluksiz rivojlanib borishi umuminsoniy demokratik qadriyatlar ta'sirining kuchayishi, jahonda xalqaro tolerantlikning barqarorligi bilan bog'liqdir. Bugungi kunda yurtimizda 130 dan ziyod millat va elat vakillarining o'zaro ahil, tinch-totuv yashab kelayotgani, Vatan va mamlakatning gullab-yashnashi uchun bir yoqadan bosh chiqarib mehnat qilayotgani internat-sionalizmning amaldagi haqiqiy ifodasidir [5].

Kundalik hayotda tolerantlik kichik ishlardan boshlanadi. Masalan, qo'shning boshqa millatdan bo'lishiga qaramay, unga hurmat ko'rsatish muhimdir. Bu ijtimoiy aloqalarni mustahkamlaydi. Maktablarda tolerantlikni o'rgatish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bolalar kichik yoshdan turli madaniyatlarni hurmat qilishni o'rganadi. Bu kelajakda ularni ochiq fikrli shaxs sifatida shakllantiradi. Ish joyida tolerantlik jamoaviy muvaffaqiyatga yordam beradi. Turli xil odamlarning g'oyalari birlashganda, yangi yechimlar topiladi. Bu innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantiradi [12].

Xullas, bag'rikenglik inson hayotini boyitadi, chunki boshqa odamlarga samimiy qiziqish, ularni tushunish istagi dunyoqarashni kengaytiradi, dunyoni barcha ko'rinishlarida bilish istagini rivojlantiradi, bebaho hayotiy tajribani to'playdi.

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ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY: MODERN APPROACHES AND CHALLENGES

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Annotation: This article explores the theoretical and practical foundations of English language teaching methodology, modern approaches, and the integration of innovative technologies. It highlights the benefits of communicative language teaching, task-based learning, the audio-lingual method, and blended learning. The paper also addresses challenges in English language teaching and provides recommendations for overcoming them.

Keywords: English language, teaching methodology, communicative approach, task-based learning, blended learning, innovative technologies.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasining nazariy va amaliy asoslari, zamonaviy yondashuvlar hamda innovatsion texnologiyalarning qo'llanishi yoritiladi. Unda kommunikativ til o'qitish, vazifa asosida ta'lim, audio-lingval metod va aralash ta'limning afzalliklari ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, ingliz tili ta'limida uchraydigan muammolar ko'rib chiqilib, ularni hal etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, o'qitish metodikasi, kommunikativ yondashuv, vazifa asosida o'qitish, aralash ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiyalar.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические основы методики преподавания английского языка, современные подходы и применение инновационных технологий. Подчеркиваются преимущества коммуникативного обучения, обучения на основе заданий, аудиолингвального метода и смешанного обучения. Кроме того, анализируются проблемы, возникающие в процессе преподавания английского языка, и даются рекомендации по их решению.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, методика преподавания, коммуникативный подход, обучение на основе заданий, смешанное обучение, инновационные технологии.

In the age of globalization, English has become the primary language of international communication, science, and technology. As a result, English language teaching (ELT) plays a crucial role in preparing learners for academic success, professional growth, and intercultural communication. The methodology of teaching English is not limited to grammar and vocabulary instruction; rather, it aims to develop communicative competence, critical thinking, and adaptability.

English language teaching methodology is based on key principles such as communicative practice, integration of all language skills, and step-by-step progression [1]. In my view, these principles make English teaching more systematic and effective, as they create a solid foundation for learners. Without such principles, language teaching risks becoming fragmented and unbalanced. Moreover, they ensure that students gradually achieve fluency without being overwhelmed at the beginning stages.

Modern approaches include Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which focuses on meaningful interaction, and Task-Based Learning (TBL), where learners solve real-life problems through language use [2]. Personally, I believe these methods are especially effective because they help students link classroom activities with real-world communication. When learners see the practical value of what they are studying, motivation increases. Furthermore, these approaches promote creativity and independent thinking, which are crucial skills in modern education.

The Audio-Lingual Method still remains effective for practicing pronunciation and grammar, while Blended Learning combines traditional classroom activities with digital resources [3]. In my opinion, although the audio-lingual method is sometimes criticized as outdated, it still has pedagogical value, especially for beginners. On the other hand, blended learning is the best reflection of today's educational reality. It allows teachers to save time, personalize learning, and combine the strengths of both traditional and online methods.

Technology is now an inseparable part of ELT. Online platforms like *Duolingo*, *Quizlet*, and *Moodle* help learners practice independently, while artificial intelligence supports personalized learning experiences [4]. I think technology makes English learning more democratic and accessible, since students can study anywhere and anytime. However, its efficiency depends on how teachers integrate these tools into lessons. Simply adding technology without pedagogical purpose does not guarantee success. Therefore, teacher training on digital literacy should be a priority.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain. Outdated textbooks, insufficient teacher training, and limited access to digital tools affect the quality of ELT in many regions. To overcome these issues, it is important to adopt internationally recognized materials, organize continuous professional development programs, and improve digital infrastructure [5]. From my perspective, these challenges cannot be solved overnight, but consistent reforms and investments will bring gradual improvement. Teacher motivation also plays a decisive role: without encouraging teachers to innovate, even the best materials and technologies may fail to achieve their potential.

In conclusion, English language teaching methodology must adapt to modern educational demands by integrating classical pedagogical principles with innovative technologies. Effective methodology should not only build grammatical and lexical knowledge but also enhance learners' communicative competence and intercultural awareness. By applying communicative, task-based, and blended methods alongside digital innovations, English teaching can better prepare students for success in the globalized world. The combination of theory, practice, and personal reflection shows that ELT is not static but dynamic, and its future depends on continuous adaptation and creativity.

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CONTEXTUALIZING WESTERN ESL PEDAGOGIES: ADAPTING COMMUNICATIVE AND TASK-BASED APPROACHES TO THE UZBEK CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT

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Annotation. This paper explores the adaptation of Western English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching methods-particularly Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)-to the Uzbek cultural and educational context. While Western ESL pedagogy emphasizes learner autonomy, interaction, and authentic communication, these principles often conflict with local traditions of teacher-centered instruction and exam-oriented learning. The study argues that effective language education in Uzbekistan requires not mere adoption, but thoughtful localization of Western practices to align with social norms, student expectations, and institutional realities.

Keywords: ESL methods, Communicative Language Teaching, Task-Based Learning, localization, Uzbek education, cultural adaptation

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada G‘arb davlatlarida keng qo‘llaniladigan ingliz tili o‘qitish uslublari -xususan, kommunikativ va topshiriqqa asoslangan o‘qitish yondashuvlarini O‘zbekiston madaniy hamda ta‘lim tizimi sharoitiga moslashtirish masalasi yoritiladi. G‘arb ESL yondashuvlari o‘quvchining mustaqilligi, faol muloqoti va haqiqiy kommunikatsiyani asosiy qadriyat sifatida ilgari suradi, biroq bu tamoyillar O‘zbekiston ta‘lim an‘analari, o‘qituvchiga yo‘naltirilgan darslar va testga tayyorlov tizimi bilan ba‘zan zid keladi. Maqolada samarali ingliz tili ta‘limi uchun G‘arb tajribasini bevosita emas, balki mahalliy sharoit va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarga moslashtirib qo‘llash zarurligi ta‘kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ESL metodlari, kommunikativ o‘qitish, topshiriqqa asoslangan ta‘lim, moslashtirish, O‘zbekiston ta‘limi, madaniy moslashuv

The spread of English as a global language has made Western ESL methodologies like Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) widely influential. These methods focus on communication, learner independence, and authentic interaction, rather than memorization or grammar drills. However, when applied in Uzbekistan, they often face challenges rooted in traditional teacher-centered education. Uzbek classrooms typically emphasize structure, discipline, and exams, where teachers dominate and students play a passive role. Such a model contrasts with CLT, which requires students to speak freely, collaborate, and participate actively. Moreover, English learning in Uzbekistan still prioritizes grammatical accuracy over communicative competence. As Richards and Rodgers note, “successful implementation of communicative methodologies depends not only on materials and techniques but on sociocultural expectations of learning” (Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching, p. 37). Hence, applying Western ESL methods in Uzbekistan demands careful cultural adaptation rather than direct imitation. This paper explores how communicative principles can be localized to align with Uzbek educational traditions while preserving their core pedagogical value.

Western ESL pedagogy, especially through Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), emphasizes meaningful interaction and the practical use of language. These methods emerged as a response to the grammar-translation and audio-lingual methods that once dominated classrooms. CLT views language learning as a social act, where communication is both the goal and the means of instruction. Learners develop competence through problem-solving, pair work, and real-life simulations rather than mechanical repetition. TBLT extends this idea by organizing lessons around communicative

tasks that reflect real-world language use—such as planning a trip, conducting an interview, or solving a classroom problem. According to Ellis, task-based learning promotes “negotiation of meaning,” helping students internalize grammar naturally while focusing on message delivery rather than form (Ellis, *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*, p. 29). These methods encourage autonomy, creativity, and fluency—skills essential for modern communication. However, such learner-centered practices assume an educational culture where students are comfortable taking initiative and expressing individual opinions—conditions not always present in Uzbek classrooms. Therefore, understanding how these methods can be balanced with local norms is crucial for effective implementation.

Applying Western ESL methods in Uzbekistan presents both cultural and institutional challenges. The local education system has long been characterized by teacher-centered instruction, where teachers are viewed as authority figures and students as passive recipients of knowledge. This tradition reflects broader cultural values of respect, hierarchy, and collective harmony. While these norms create disciplined classrooms, they can limit student participation and creativity, which are key aspects of communicative learning. Furthermore, many teachers were trained in grammar-translation methods, emphasizing accuracy and test preparation over fluency and interaction. As a result, lessons often focus on textbook exercises and error correction rather than spontaneous communication. According to Littlewood, successful communication-based learning requires “a shift in both teacher and learner roles—from authority and dependency to guidance and autonomy” (*Communicative Language Teaching: An Introduction*, p. 46). However, this shift may be uncomfortable for students unaccustomed to speaking openly or challenging ideas. Institutional constraints also play a role. Large class sizes, limited access to authentic materials, and exam-driven curricula make it difficult to apply communicative or task-based strategies effectively. Teachers must often adapt these methods creatively to local realities—using simpler activities, integrating group work gradually, or aligning communicative tasks with exam content. Thus, cultural and systemic adaptation becomes as essential as linguistic training in ensuring the success of ESL instruction in Uzbekistan.

For communicative and task-based approaches to work in Uzbekistan, adaptation—not imitation—is essential. Teachers can preserve the core goals of interaction and fluency while reshaping classroom practices to fit local expectations. For example, instead of open debates or abstract discussions, communicative tasks can focus on familiar, culturally relevant topics such as family, education, or traditions. Pair and group work can also be introduced gradually. In large or formal classrooms, teachers might assign structured speaking roles or written preparation before oral practice to reduce anxiety. As Nunan notes, “task-based learning succeeds when learners see a clear link between classroom activity and real communication” (*Task-Based Language Teaching*, p. 52). Furthermore, incorporating Uzbek examples, proverbs, and social contexts into tasks helps students connect language with their identity. This localization creates balance—students still learn to communicate effectively in English, but within a framework that feels natural and culturally respectful.

A balanced, hybrid approach may offer the best solution for ESL teaching in Uzbekistan. Instead of fully replacing traditional instruction with Western models, educators can blend communicative principles with local teaching strengths. This means keeping structured grammar lessons for accuracy while adding interactive tasks to build fluency. Teachers act as both guides and authorities, helping students gain confidence while maintaining classroom discipline. As Brown notes, “effective pedagogy lies in the ability to adapt methods to the needs, abilities, and cultures of learners” (*Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*, p. 61). By combining Western flexibility with Uzbek educational

discipline, a culturally responsive model can emerge—one that promotes both communicative competence and academic rigor.

Adapting Western ESL methods to the Uzbek context is not about rejecting or imitating, but about balancing global pedagogical values with local realities. Communicative and task-based approaches bring valuable emphasis on interaction, autonomy, and fluency, yet their success depends on cultural sensitivity and institutional readiness. Teachers in Uzbekistan must act as mediators between two traditions—retaining the structure and respect of the local classroom while fostering open communication and learner participation. A hybrid model that merges Western innovation with Uzbek educational discipline can lead to more meaningful, confident, and culturally grounded language learning. Ultimately, localization, not imitation, ensures that ESL teaching becomes both effective and authentic in the Uzbek setting.

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THE PRIMACY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract: This article discusses the significance of psychological factors in language learning. Motivation, a positive emotional state, and self-confidence facilitate effective acquisition, whereas stress and anxiety create barriers. Furthermore, a supportive atmosphere and active communication help learners overcome psychological obstacles and accelerate the learning process. In conclusion, psychological factors often play a more crucial role than grammar rules and vocabulary knowledge.

Key words: psychological factors, language learning, motivation, self-confidence, anxiety, communication.

Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждается значение психологических факторов в изучении языка. Мотивация, позитивный эмоциональный настрой и уверенность в себе способствуют эффективному усвоению, в то время как стресс и тревога создают препятствия. Более того, благоприятная атмосфера и активное общение помогают учащимся преодолевать психологические препятствия и ускорять процесс обучения. В заключение следует отметить, что психологические факторы часто играют более важную роль, чем грамматические правила и знание лексики.

Ключевые слова: психологические факторы, изучение языка, мотивация, уверенность в себе, тревожность, общение

Annotatsiya: Maqolada til o'rganishda psixologik omillarning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Motivatsiya, ijobiy ruhiy holat va o'ziga ishonch yangi tilni samarali o'zlashtirishni osonlashtiradi, stress va xavotir esa to'siq bo'lishi mumkin. Shuningdek, o'quvchi o'zini erkin his qiladigan muhit va faol muloqot tilni tezroq o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, psixologik omillar ko'pincha grammatik qoidalar va lug'atdan ham muhimroq rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: psixologik omillar, til o'rganish, motivatsiya, o'ziga ishonch, xavotir, muloqot.

Krashen emphasizes that grammar and vocabulary alone are not enough for language learning. According to his theory, learners need to be exposed to comprehensible input. But even more important is the learner's psychological state. If the learner feels insecure, anxious, or stressed, their "affective filter" becomes high, blocking language acquisition. On the other hand, if the learner feels calm, motivated, and confident, the "affective filter" is low, and learning becomes faster and more effective. "In language learning, the learner's emotional state plays a decisive role. If the learner studies with fear and stress, the input does not reach the brain. But if the learner feels free, confident, and motivated, they acquire the language naturally and effectively." Long believes that the most important factor in language learning is interaction. He explains the process of "negotiation of meaning." For example, when two people communicate and one does not understand something, they ask for clarification, explanations, or corrections. Through this process, learners not only improve their grammar and vocabulary but also learn to feel psychologically free in communication. During communication, learners notice their mistakes, correct them, and acquire the language more effectively. A learner who feels psychologically free gains more from this experience. Researchers on Psychological Factors (motivation, anxiety, self-confidence) Khajavy et al. (2019): Their study shows that "psychological capital" (motivation, positive thinking, and self-confidence) directly influences success in language learning. Positive Psychology approach: When the learning environment is friendly, joyful, and stress-free, students participate more actively and learn more effectively.

Most people have suffered with English for so long they worry there is no solution. Trained by schools to be passive, fear mistakes, and search for just one right answer, most English learners are stressed and frustrated. Some feel nearly hopeless. They have spent years in English classrooms. They have spent years memorizing grammar rules and vocabulary lists. They have spent years studying for exams such as the TOEFL, IELTS, or TOEIC. Despite all this work and effort, most English learners are frustrated. Many struggle with even simple conversations. Many feel nervous any time they must speak English. They have memorized countless grammar rules, yet even simple conversations feel difficult. Likewise, despite years of study, most learners still cannot understand American TV or movies. After so many years of traditional learning, students are confused. When they try to speak, they constantly think about grammar and translations. First they think of a sentence in their own language, then they translate it to English, then they think about the grammar, and finally they speak. When they listen, they go through a similar process. They hear the English, translate it into their own language, think of a response in their own language, translate their response into English, and then think about the grammar to be sure their response is correct. No wonder their speech is so slow and unnatural! No wonder English feels so stressful and difficult! Real conversations are fast, and it's nearly impossible to do all of this thinking fast enough, especially when talking to a native speaker. If you think about translations and grammar during a real conversation, you will quickly become lost. Instead of listening carefully to the other person, you'll be translating your own responses and trying to remember grammar. Your

speech will be hesitant. Often, the other person will become frustrated by your lack of understanding. Of course, if you see the other person is losing patience, you will usually become even more nervous. It's a terrible downward spiral that most English learners know too well. There is a solution. There is a way to escape the hidden curriculum. There is a road to English fluency and you can travel on it. You can speak English powerfully. You can speak English clearly, naturally, and effortlessly. This solution, however, will require you to completely change your beliefs about education and completely change the way you learn English. I call the solution the Effortless English™ system and it has two parts: the psychology and the method. Most schools, most teachers, and most learners focus only on method. In other words, they are solely focused on the pieces of the English language - vocabulary and grammar. As we learned in the last chapter, schools primarily use the "grammar translation" method, with some "communication activities" added. While schools are focused just on method, they completely ignore the first part of the Effortless English™ system - the psychology. Yet, psychology is probably the most important element for success with English speaking. When you think of your own English speaking, you'll realize that your nervousness, lack of confidence, and frustration are major problems. How do you change these? Without an effective psychological system, you will struggle to find success with even the best language teaching method. Let's use a story to understand these two important parts of the Effortless English™ system. Imagine that you are on a road. You are driving on the road to English fluency.

In fact, you probably will not reach your destination. Now, you could put some high quality gas in that old car, but even then it will likely take you a long time to reach your destination. Better gas will help a little, but the trip is still likely to be slow and frustrating. Now imagine instead that you'll be driving a Formula 1 racing car on this road to fluency. This car is made for speed and performance. Clearly, it will go faster than the old, slow car. But what if you fill it up with cheap, low quality fuel? There will likely be problems. Racing cars need racing fuel or they will not perform well. Obviously, the best situation would be to put high quality racing fuel into your Formula 1 racing car! With this car and this fuel, your trip on the road to fluency will be fast and exciting. This is how learning English works. If you've been studying for a while, you know by now that there are all sorts of systems. Traditional classes at universities. (pp. 413–468)

Private lessons from language schools. Online or packaged software courses. Immersion programs that put you in the country where they speak the language you're studying. In other words, you've got a lot of different cars to choose from. Some may be better than others, some may be faster. But even the greatest of these methods, the Ferrari of language teaching, if you will, needs fuel to make it work. A method, after all, is only an engine. And if you don't give an engine the proper fuel, even a great one won't work the way you'd like it to. To succeed, you need both quality fuel and a powerful engine. The right engine + the right fuel = success Obviously, I believe the right engine would be the Effortless English™ system. What is the fuel? The fuel is your psychology. It is the beliefs, emotions, and goals that power your learning. Your fuel is your motivation, your confidence, your energy, your enthusiasm. (pp 119–142)

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ENHANCING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS: EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR FLUENCY AND CONFIDENCE

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Annotation. Learning a foreign language has become increasingly vital in today’s modern world. In language acquisition, four key skills – listening, speaking, reading and writing – each play a significant role. This article examines various approaches to enhance these skills with a particular focus on speaking. Several strategies are discussed, supported by practical tips and personal experience to provide a comprehensive guide for improving spoken English.

Keywords: English speaking skills, language learning, fluency, vocabulary development, pronunciation, communication techniques, active listening, confidence - building, daily practice, second language acquisition.

Аннотация. Изучение иностранного языка становится всё более важным в современном мире. В освоении языка четыре ключевых навыка - аудирование, говорение, чтение и письмо – играют важную роль. В данной статье рассматриваются различные подходы к развитию этих навыков, уделяя особое внимание говорению. В статье рассматриваются несколько стратегий, подкреплённых практическими советами и личным опытом, которые представляют собой комплексное руководство по улучшению разговорного английского языка.

Ключевые слова: навыки говорения на английском языке, изучение языка, беглость речи, развитие словарного запаса, произношение, коммуникативные техники, активное слушание, укрепление уверенности в себе, ежедневная практика, освоение второго языка.

Annotatsiya. Chet tilini o‘rganish bugungi zamonaviy dunyoda tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tilni o‘zlashtirishda to‘rtta asosiy qobiliyat - tinglash, gapirish, o‘qish va yozish - har biri muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ushbu maqola nutqqa alohida e‘tibor qaratgan holda ushbu ko‘nikmalarni oshirish uchun turli yondashuvlarni ko‘rib chiqadi. Og‘zaki ingliz tilini yaxshilash bo‘yicha keng qamrovli qo‘llanmani taqdim etish uchun amaliy maslahatlar va shaxsiy tajriba bilan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadigan bir nechta strategiyalar muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ingliz tilida so‘zlash qobiliyati, til o‘rganish, ravonlik, so‘z boyligini rivojlantirish, talaffuz, muloqot qilish texnikasi, faol tinglash, ishonch - mustahkamlash, kundalik amaliyot, ikkinchi tilni o‘zlashtirish.

In delivering an effective speech, speaking skills play a crucial role and many individuals strive to improve this area. As the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated:” It is time to establish a solid foundation for the future in teaching foreign languages. Language is an essential and powerful tool for any society.

Improving English speaking skills requires consistent practice, the right strategies and a willingness to overcome challenges. In this article I will explore effective methods to boost oral English, ranging from daily practice techniques to confidence – building ways for better communication.

One of the most effective ways to improve English speaking skills is to speak as often as possible. Many learners hesitate, have some fear of making mistakes during the process. However, fluency is built through practice, not perfection, James Joyce once said: “Mistakes are the portals of discovery.” This means that every mistake we make is an absolutely opportunity to get more knowledge and grow. A useful technique is called a “self-practice”. Speaking to oneself in English, whether by narrating daily routines or expressing thoughts out loud, assists to build confidence. Making a speech in front of a mirror and practicing conversations is likely to improve body language and pronunciation. Additionally, recording oneself and listening to the playback allows learners to identify fields for development.

Attending English-speaking clubs for participating in discussion groups is another productive way to fortify speaking skills. Interacting with native speakers through language exchange programs or online platforms such as Tandem and Hello Talk can provide real-world practice opportunities. As Nelson Mandela wisely stated: "If you talk to a man in a language he understands, that goes to his head. If you talk to him in his own language that goes to his heart." Practicing English with native speakers assists to develop natural pronunciation, intonation and cultural understanding

A strong vocabulary is the foundation of successful speaking. Without sufficient words, expressing thoughts becomes really challenging. Frank Smith truly said: "One language sets you in a corridor for life. Two languages open every door along the way." Learning new words not only improves fluency but also strengthens comprehension and expression.

Reading books, newspapers and online articles in English is a great way to encounter new words in context. Keeping a vocabulary journal and writing down new phrases along with their meanings and example sentences help in retention. Moreover, using new words in conversations ensures that they become a part of active vocabulary.

Utilizing synonyms and antonyms while practicing can also boost expression. For instance, instead of always saying "good", one can use "excellent", "remarkable", or "outstanding" depending on the situation. As Mark Twain said: "The difference between the right word is the difference between lightning and a lightning bug."

One major barrier to fluency is the habit of thinking in one’s native language and then translating into English before speaking. This slows down communication and often results in unnatural sentences. Federico Fellini stated: "A different language is different vision of life." Thinking in English not only develops proficiency but also provides understanding the language from a natural perspective.

To develop this habit, learners can launch by labeling objects in their surroundings in English. Another technique is mental narration - describing actions, thoughts and feelings in English throughout the day. Writing journals or social media post in English also helps in training the brain to process information in the language directly.

Listening and speaking are closely related. A person who listens attentively to native speakers can learn pronunciation, sentence structure and natural expressions. Oscar Wilde once said: "Be yourself, everyone else is already taken," and this applies to language learning as well-imitating native speakers is beneficial, but developing one’s own speaking style is just as important. Watching English movies, listening to podcasts and engaging with English-speaking media allow learners to become familiar with the rhythm and flow of the language.

Repeating dialogues from movies or TV shows and shadowing the speech of native speakers can be an influential way to upgrade pronunciation and intonation.

Mastering spoken English is a gradual process that requires dedication, practice and patience. By speaking regularly, expanding vocabulary, thinking in English, listening to native speakers, engaging in real conversations and overcoming fear, beginners can enhance proficiency and confidence.

Language is not just a means of communication, it is a tool for personal and professional growth. Angela Carter said: "Language is power, life, and the instrument of culture, the instrument of domination and liberation." Learning English has an access to open you a world of amenities, allowing individuals to connect with people, express concepts and explore innovative possibilities.

In the end, the key to influence is perseverance. As Winston Churchill once mentioned: "Continuous effort-not strength or intelligence- is the key to unlocking our potential." With continuous effort and a fearless attitude, anyone can become a confident English speaker.

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INTEGRATING THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: EQUIVALENCE, PRAGMATICS, SEMIOTICS, AND LINGUISTIC APPROACHES

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Abstract. This article explores key theoretical and conceptual approaches in translation studies, focusing on four interconnected dimensions: linguistic equivalence, pragmatics, semiotics, and the tension between structural and functional linguistics. It examines the challenges of achieving equivalence across languages, the role of pragmatic context in shaping translation choices, the semiotic perspective on signs and cultural codes, and the contrast between formal-structural and functional approaches to meaning in translation. By reviewing seminal works and recent developments, the paper argues that an integrative framework that combines structural rigor with functional sensitivity is most promising for dealing with the complexities of translation in multicultural and multimodal contexts.

Keywords: translation studies; linguistic equivalence; pragmatics; semiotics; structural linguistics; functional linguistics; intercultural communication

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются ключевые теоретические и концептуальные подходы в исследованиях перевода, уделяя особое внимание четырём взаимосвязанным измерениям: лингвистической эквивалентности, прагматике, семиотике и противоречиям между структурной и функциональной лингвистикой. В статье рассматриваются проблемы достижения эквивалентности между языками, роль прагматического контекста в формировании выбора при переводе, семиотический подход к знакам и культурным кодам, а также различия между формально-структурным и функциональным подходами к значению в переводе. Анализируя основополагающие работы и последние разработки, в статье утверждается, что интегративная концепция, сочетающая структурную строгость с функциональной чувствительностью, наиболее перспективна для решения сложных задач перевода в мультикультурных и мультимодальных контекстах.

Ключевые слова: исследования перевода; лингвистической эквивалентности; прагматика; семиотика; структурная лингвистика; функциональная лингвистика; межкультурная коммуникация

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola tarjima nazariyasidagi muhim nazariy va tushuncha yondashuvlarini tadqiq qiladi; ayniqsa to'rt bir-biri bilan bog'liq o'lchovga e'tibor qaratadi: lingvistik ekvivalentlik, pragmatika, semiotika va struktural hamda funksional tilshunoslik orasidagi muvozanat. Maqolada tillararo ekvivalentlikni ta'minlashdagi muammolar, tarjima qarorlarida pragmatik kontekstning roli, belgilar va madaniy kodlarga semiotik nuqtai nazar, hamda tarjimada ma'no va vazifaga nisbatan struktural va funksional yondashuvlarning farqlari tahlil qilinadi. Asosiy nazariy ishlanmalar va so'nggi rivojlanishlar orqali maqola shuni taklif qiladi: struktural nazariyaning aniqligi bilan funksional sezgirlikni birlashtirgan integrativ yondashuv ko'p madaniyatli va multimodal kontekstlarda tarjima muammolarini hal qilish uchun istiqbolli bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: tarjima tadqiqotlari; lingvistik ekvivalentlik; pragmatika; semiotika; strukturaviy tilshunoslik; funksional tilshunoslik; madaniyatlararo muloqot

Translation studies, as an interdisciplinary field, investigate how meaning, form, and function are transferred across languages and cultures. Among its most influential theoretical perspectives are linguistic equivalence, which explores the problem of matching meaning between languages; pragmatics, which highlights the role of context and communicative intent; semiotics, which examines signs and cultural codes; and the contrast between structural and functional linguistics, which addresses the tension between form and function in translation. This paper critically analyses these four conceptual approaches, discussing their challenges, possibilities, and implications for modern translation practice.

Equivalence has long been a central issue in translation theory, yet it remains one of the most contested concepts. Eugene Nida (1964) introduced the distinction between formal equivalence, which aims to preserve the linguistic form and structure of the source text, and dynamic equivalence, which seeks to reproduce the same effect on the target audience as the original text produced on its readers. J. C. Catford (1965) also discussed equivalence at different linguistic levels, such as lexical, grammatical, and textual, emphasizing that translation involves systematic shifts when exact correspondence is not possible. However, achieving true equivalence is highly problematic. Languages encode reality in different ways, and cultural concepts often have no direct counterparts. For example, idiomatic expressions like the English phrase "spill the beans" cannot be translated literally without losing meaning. In such cases, translators must choose between preserving the source form and ensuring communicative effectiveness in the target language.

Pragmatics examines how meaning is shaped by context, intention, and interaction, which makes it a key element in translation. A literal transfer of words is often insufficient because language functions within cultural and situational frameworks. For example, the phrase “Can you open the window?” in English is pragmatically understood as a polite request rather than a real inquiry about ability. Without this awareness, the translator risks misrepresenting the speaker’s intention. Speech act theory (Searle, 1969) highlights that utterances perform actions such as requesting, promising, or commanding. These acts may not correspond directly across languages, so the translator must reproduce the same communicative effect in the target culture. Hatim and Mason (1990) also emphasize the importance of pragmatic equivalence, where meaning is transferred not just semantically but functionally, according to context.

In short, pragmatics reminds us that translation is more than words—it is the transfer of communicative intentions shaped by cultural and situational norms. Modern translation scholars, such as Munday (2016), argue that equivalence should be viewed as a flexible and functional concept rather than an absolute one. The primary goal of the translator is not to mirror every linguistic element but to deliver meaning in a way that fulfills the communicative purpose. This shift toward functional adequacy reflects a broader understanding of translation as a dynamic and intercultural act rather than a purely linguistic substitution.

Semiotics, the study of signs and symbols, expands translation beyond linguistics to include cultural codes. A word, color, or gesture may represent one meaning in one culture and something entirely different in another. For instance, the color white symbolizes purity in many Western societies but mourning in some Asian contexts. Translators must therefore interpret these signs carefully and adjust them to convey the correct meaning for the target audience. Eco (1976) argues that translation is inherently semiotic because it involves the interpretation of sign systems and their transfer between cultures. This means that translators act not only as linguistic mediators but also as interpreters of cultural meaning. By applying semiotic awareness, translators ensure that the message resonates with the intended audience and preserves its symbolic value.

Structural linguistics views translation as the transfer of grammatical and lexical patterns from one language to another. It emphasizes form, syntax, and rules, aiming for structural equivalence (Catford, 1965). However, this approach often overlooks cultural and communicative aspects. Functional linguistics, on the other hand, highlights how language is shaped by context and social use. Halliday (1994) argues that meaning depends on function—how a text informs, persuades, or interacts with its audience. From this view, successful translation is not only about accuracy in form but also about reproducing communicative purpose. In practice, translators balance both approaches: preserving structural clarity while ensuring that the translation fulfills the same function for the target audience.

Theoretical and conceptual approaches in translation studies show that translation is more than a mechanical process of replacing words. Linguistic equivalence stresses structural and semantic accuracy, pragmatics focuses on intention and context, semiotics reveals the role of cultural signs, and functional linguistics highlights communicative purpose. Together, these perspectives demonstrate that effective translation requires a balance between linguistic form and cultural meaning. By integrating these approaches, translators act as both language specialists and cultural mediators. This multidimensional view strengthens translation studies as a discipline and ensures that translation continues to serve as a bridge across languages and cultures.

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BOLALAR NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MULTIMEDIA TEKNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida multimedia texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning imkoniyatlari yoritilgan. Maqolada interaktiv audio-vizual vositalar, raqamli o‘yinlar, multimedia kartochkalar va video materiallar orqali bolalarning so‘z boyligini oshirish, talaffuzni shakllantirish, og‘zaki nutqni mustahkamlash hamda muloqot ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish yo‘llari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy multimedia vositalarining pedagogik samaradorligi, tarbiyachining roli va individual yondashuv orqali nutqiy rivojlanishni ta‘minlash masalalari ham ko‘rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: nutq rivoji, multimedia texnologiyalari, og‘zaki muloqot, so‘z boyligi, talaffuz, kommunikativ kompetensiya, tarbiyachi, interaktiv metod, audio-vizual vositalar, ta‘lim texnologiyasi.

Abstract: This article highlights the potential of using multimedia technologies in the process of developing speech among preschool-aged children. It analyzes how interactive audio-visual tools, digital games, multimedia flashcards, and video materials can enhance children’s vocabulary, pronunciation, oral speech, and communication skills. Furthermore, the paper examines the pedagogical effectiveness of modern multimedia tools, the teacher’s role, and the importance of an individualized approach in fostering children’s speech development.

Keywords: speech development, multimedia technologies, oral communication, vocabulary, pronunciation, communicative competence, educator, interactive method, audio-visual tools, educational technology.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности использования мультимедийных технологий в процессе развития речи у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируются способы обогащения словарного запаса, формирования произношения, укрепления устной речи и развития коммуникативных навыков с помощью интерактивных аудиовизуальных средств, цифровых игр, мультимедийных карточек и видеоматериалов. Также рассматриваются педагогическая эффективность современных мультимедийных средств, роль воспитателя и значение индивидуального подхода в обеспечении речевого развития.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи, мультимедийные технологии, устное общение, словарный запас, произношение, коммуникативная компетенция, воспитатель, интерактивный метод, аудиовизуальные средства, образовательные технологии.

Maqtabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayoni bolaning fikrlash, muloqot qilish va o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etish qobiliyatini shakllantirishning eng muhim bosqichi bo'lib, bugungi kunda multimedia texnologiyalari ushbu jarayonda samarali vosita sifatida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Interaktiv audio-vizual o'yinlar, raqamli kartochkalar, video ertaklar va animatsiyalar bolalarda so'z boyligini oshirish, talaffuzni shakllantirish, grammatik tuzilishni mustahkamlash va og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi [1]. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, multimedia vositalari bolalarning diqqatini jamlash, e'tibor va konsentratsiyani oshirish, shuningdek, nutqdagi xatolarni erkin tuzatish va mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi [1]. Til o'yinlari, dramatik mashg'ulotlar, interaktiv dasturlar va video ertaklar bolalarda jumla tuzilishi, ifodalilik va muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantiradi, yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirish va ularni kontekstda ishlatish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi [2]. Shu bilan birga, multimedia texnologiyalari bolalarning hissiy holatini ijobiy saqlashga yordam beradi, qo'rquv va tortinish hissini kamaytiradi, o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etish imkonini yaratadi hamda ijodiy fikrlashni rag'batlantiradi [1]. Tarbiyachi multimedia vositalaridan foydalangan holda bolaning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan individual yondashuvni tatbiq etadi, interaktiv o'yinlar va audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar orqali nutqiy, ijtimoiy va hissiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, muammoli vaziyatlarda mustaqil qaror qabul qilish va mantiqiy tafakkurini shakllantiradi [3]. Masalan, "Rasm orqali hikoya tuzish" o'yini bolalarda so'z boyligini kengaytiradi, jumla tuzilishini mustahkamlaydi va muloqotga rag'batlantiradi, shuningdek, bolalarni kreativlik va ijodiy fikrlashga undaydi [3].

Multimedia kartochkalar va interaktiv audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar bolalarga tovushlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qilishni osonlashtiradi, yangi so'zlarni eslab qolishga yordam beradi va nutqni ifodali qilish ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi [4]. Shuningdek, zamonaviy raqamli dasturlar bolalarning ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi: rolli o'yinlar orqali ular muloqot madaniyati, jamoaviy ishlarni bajarish, muammoli vaziyatlarda muloqot qilish va boshqalar bilan hamkorlik qilishni o'rganadi. Multimedia vositalari bolaning nutqiy kompetensiyasini oshirish bilan birga, uning intellektual, ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishini uyg'unlashtiradi, bolani faol muloqotga jalb qiladi, interaktiv o'yinlar orqali motivatsiyasini oshiradi va mustaqil fikrlashni rag'batlantiradi. Shu tariqa, multimedia texnologiyalari yordamida tarbiyachi bolalarni individual yondashuv asosida rivojlantiradi, nutqiy, hissiy va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi, bolani keyingi ta'lim bosqichlariga tayyorlaydi, muloqot madaniyati va interaktiv fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi, shuningdek, bolaning ijodiy salohiyati va o'z fikriga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi. Multimedia vositalari nafaqat nutqni rivojlantirishga, balki bolalarning mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash, jamoaviy ishlar va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga, ijtimoiy muhitga moslashuvchanlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi [5].

Shu bilan birga, interaktiv audio-vizual mashg'ulotlar bolalarni zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan ishlashga o'rgatadi, ularni ta'lim jarayonida faol qatnashishga undaydi va mustaqil o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi, bu esa ularning kelajakdagi ta'lim va ijtimoiy hayotga tayyorgarligini mustahkamlaydi. Multimedia vositalari yordamida nutqiy va kommunikativ kompetensiya rivoji nafaqat samarali, balki keng qamrovli bo'lib, individual yondashuvni qo'llashga imkon yaratadi va bolalarning ta'lim jarayonidagi muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlaydi [1].

Shu tariqa, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida multimedia texnologiyalari nafaqat pedagogik vosita, balki bolalarning ijtimoiy, hissiy va intellektual rivojlanishi uchun muhim strategik vosita sifatida alohida ahamiyatga ega.

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DEVELOPING L2 LISTENING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article explores the importance of listening for specific information in second language (L2) learning and teaching. It discusses major challenges learners face when developing this subskill and presents effective strategies teachers can use to support them. The paper emphasizes the role of explicit instruction, metacognitive awareness, and scaffolded practice in improving learners’ listening comprehension. It concludes with several practical classroom recommendations for teachers and suggestions for further study.

Keywords: listening comprehension, L2 learning, specific information, scaffolding, metacognitive strategies

Listening is one of the most essential skills in language learning, and among its subskills, listening for specific information plays a particularly vital role. This type of listening involves focusing on concrete details such as names, numbers, dates, or specific facts within spoken language, which are crucial for real-life situations like understanding announcements, following directions, or answering comprehension questions during exams. Many learners struggle with this skill because they attempt to understand every word instead of focusing on key information. Research indicates that rapid speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, and a lack of effective listening strategies are major obstacles [1]. Therefore, teachers must guide learners in developing techniques that allow them to identify essential details efficiently. Listening for specific information differs from global listening, which focuses on the overall meaning of a text. In detail-oriented listening, learners must attend to precise elements such as time, location, or quantity. However, they often face difficulties due to the fast pace of speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, or the inability to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant information. To address these challenges, teachers can train learners to predict what they will hear, identify signal words such as first, next, and finally, and take brief notes of key points. Effective teaching of this subskill requires a combination of explicit strategy instruction, scaffolded practice, and reflective learning.

Explicit strategy instruction involves teachers modeling listening processes—previewing questions, predicting answers, and checking comprehension—to help students approach listening tasks strategically. Scaffolded listening tasks provide guided support through techniques such as dividing recordings into shorter parts, replaying difficult

segments, or using visual aids like charts and diagrams. These methods help learners manage cognitive load and focus on critical details. Pre-listening activities, such as discussing the topic or reviewing key vocabulary, prepare students for what they will hear and activate relevant background knowledge. During listening, students can focus on specific elements such as names, dates, or numbers while using shorthand notes to capture details efficiently. Post-listening reflection allows learners to analyze which strategies were effective and encourages metacognitive awareness through discussions or short written reflections. Despite these methods, learners often report recurring challenges such as fast speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, memory limitations, distractors, and variations in pronunciation. Native speakers' rapid or reduced speech forms can make comprehension difficult, while unknown words may divert attention from the target details. In addition, keeping multiple pieces of information in working memory can overwhelm learners, particularly when dealing with long or complex passages. To overcome these difficulties, repetition, contextual learning, and gradual exposure to authentic materials are essential for improving listening proficiency. Teachers play a key role in helping students overcome these barriers and enhance their listening skills. Research and classroom experience suggest several effective techniques, including teaching prediction strategies, providing guided worksheets, using short listening materials before authentic ones, allowing multiple listening to build confidence, and incorporating reflection activities such as listening journals. Moreover, offering feedback on both results and strategy use helps learners refine their approach and develop independence. These pedagogical practices not only improve comprehension but also promote learner autonomy and confidence. Although many strategies have proven effective, no single approach works equally well for all learners. Success depends on individual factors such as proficiency level, motivation, and exposure to English outside the classroom. Future research could explore how digital listening tools, including adaptive learning apps and AI-based listening platforms, can personalize instruction and meet diverse learner needs. In conclusion, listening for specific information is a practical and essential subskill in second language learning. To help learners succeed, teachers must provide explicit strategy instruction, scaffolded tasks, and opportunities for metacognitive reflection. Through consistent practice, guided feedback, and exposure to authentic listening situations, students develop the confidence and accuracy needed to become effective listeners capable of handling academic and everyday communication.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari yoritilgan. Maqolada ijodiy tafakkurning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari, uning shakllanish bosqichlari, tarbiyachi va oila hamkorligining ahamiyati, shuningdek o'yin, san'at, ertak, tabiat bilan tanishuv, innovatsion texnologiyalar orqali ijodiy fikrlashni faollashtirish yo'llari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot jarayonida bolalarda mustaqil fikrlash, yangilik yaratish, tasavvur qilish va nostandart yechim topish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan samarali metod va yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijodiy fikrlash, maktabgacha ta'lim, bola shaxsi, tarbiyachi, o'yin faoliyati, tasavvur, innovatsion texnologiyalar, muammoli vaziyat, pedagogik yondashuv, rivojlantirish.

Abstract: This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of developing creative thinking in preschool children. It discusses the psychological and pedagogical foundations of creative thinking, its stages of formation, and the importance of cooperation between educators and families. The study also analyzes ways to enhance creativity through play, art, storytelling, nature exploration, and innovative technologies. During the research process, effective methods and approaches aimed at developing children's independent thinking, imagination, originality, and problem-solving skills are explored.

Keywords: creative thinking, preschool education, child personality, educator, play activity, imagination, innovative technologies, problem situation, pedagogical approach, development.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрываются теоретические и практические аспекты развития творческого мышления у детей дошкольного возраста. Рассматриваются психолого-педагогические основы творческого мышления, этапы его формирования, значение сотрудничества воспитателя и семьи. Также анализируются пути активизации творческого мышления через игру, искусство, сказку, знакомство с природой и использование инновационных технологий. В ходе исследования изучаются эффективные методы и подходы, направленные на развитие у детей самостоятельного мышления, воображения, способности к созданию нового и поиску нестандартных решений.

Ключевые слова: творческое мышление, дошкольное образование, личность ребёнка, воспитатель, игровая деятельность, воображение, инновационные технологии, проблемная ситуация, педагогический подход, развитие.

Bugungi kunda jamiyatda ijodiy fikrlaydigan, yangilik yarata oladigan, muammolarga nostandart yondasha oladigan shaxslarni tarbiyalash zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining eng muhim vazifalaridan biridir. Bu jarayonni esa eng erta bosqich -maktabgacha yoshdan boshlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki bola aynan shu davrda o'zini anglashni, atrofdagi dunyoni idrok etishni, mustaqil fikr yuritishni o'rganadi. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar tafakkuri hali shakllanish bosqichida bo'lgani uchun ularda ijodiylik, tasavvur, qiziqish va bilishga chanqoqlik tabiiy tarzda mavjud bo'ladi. Shu bois pedagoglarning vazifasi bu tabiiy qiziqishni so'ndirmaslik, aksincha, uni rivojlantirish uchun qulay psixologik va o'quv muhit yaratishdan iboratdir.

Ijodiy fikrlash -bu bolaning atrofdagi narsalarni o'z tajribasi asosida yangicha talqin etish, mavjud bilimlardan foydalangan holda yangi g'oyalar va yechimlar yaratish

qobiliyatidir. Bolalar ijodiy fikrlash jarayonida tasavvur, xayol, emotsiya va tafakkur birgalikda ishlaydi. Shu bois ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish maktabgacha ta'lim jarayonining asosiy tarkibiy qismiga aylanishi lozim. Ijodiy tafakkur bolaning yosh xususiyatlariga qarab bosqichma-bosqich rivojlanadi. 3–4 yoshdagi bolalar tasavvur orqali reallikni o'zicha qayta yaratadi: ular narsalarni boshqa narsaga o'xshatadi, hayvonlarga gapirtiradi, oddiy predmetlardan noodatiy vazifada foydalanadi. 5–6 yoshdagi bolalarda esa tahlil qilish, sabab-oqibat bog'liqligini tushunish, o'z fikrini asoslash, muammoli vaziyatdan chiqish kabi fikrlash elementlari paydo bo'ladi. Bu jarayonda o'yin faoliyati muhim o'rin tutadi. O'yin - bolaning tabiiy ehtiyoji bo'lib, u orqali bola atrof-muhitni anglaydi, ijtimoiy munosabatlarni o'rganadi, yangi vaziyatlarni sinovdan o'tkazadi. Rolli o'yinlar (“Do'konchi va xaridor”, “Shifokor va bemor”, “O'qituvchi va o'quvchi”) bolalarning ijtimoiy tajribasini boyitadi, ularni yangi rollarga kirishga, ijodkorlik ko'rsatishga undaydi.

Tarbiyachi o'yin jarayonida bola fikrini cheklamasdan, erkin tasavvur qilish, xatolardan qo'rqmaslik, o'z g'oyasini bildirish imkonini berishi kerak. Ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda san'atning barcha turlari – rasm, loy ishi, qo'shiq, raqs, musiqa – muhim rol o'ynaydi. Rasm chizayotgan bola nafaqat estetik didini, balki rang, shakl va fazoviy tasavvurini ham rivojlantiradi. Musiqa esa bolalarning hissiy olamini boyitadi, ritm, uyg'unlik, go'zallikni his etish qobiliyatini kuchaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, ertak terapiyasi ham ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi samarali vosita sifatida keng qo'llaniladi. Bolalarga tanish ertaklarni qayta tuzish, o'zlari ixtiro qilgan voqealarni hikoya qilish ularning fantaziyasini faollashtiradi, mantiqiy ketma-ketlikni saqlashga o'rgatadi. Tarbiyachining shaxsiy roli bu jarayonda beqiyosdir. U bolalarga ijodiy muhit yaratib beruvchi, yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatuvchi, rag'batlantiruvchi shaxs bo'lishi kerak.

Tarbiyachi har bir bolaning qobiliyatini inobatga olgan holda individual yondashuv asosida ishlasa, ijodiy tafakkur tabiiy rivojlanadi. Ijodiy muhit yaratishda quyidagi shartlar muhim: savollarga ochiq munosabatda bo'lish, har bir bolaning fikrini qadrlash, tanqid o'rniga rag'bat berish, mustaqil qaror qabul qilishga o'rgatish. Shuningdek, o'quv jarayoniga muammoli vaziyatlar kiritish –“nima bo'ladi agar...” kabi savollar bilan o'ylashga undash, mashg'ulotlarda tasviriy tahlil (bolaning rasmida qanday g'oya aks etganini so'rash), ijodiy loyihalar tayyorlash kabi usullar samaralidir. So'nggi yillarda maktabgacha ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlar, xususan,

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION O'QITISH METODLARI

O'rishova Lobar Odiljon qizi

*“Agar mendan sizni nima qiynaydi?” deb so'rasangiz,
farzandlarimning ta'lim va tarbiyasi deb javob beraman.*

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlanishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan pedagogik jarayon murakkab, shu bilan birga rang-barangdir. Ta'lim-tarbiya samaradorligiga erishishda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlaridagi har bir faoliyat turini to'g'ri tashkil qilish lozim. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish, va ularning samaradorligi haqida bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti, zamonaviy yondashuv, innovatsiya, tarbiyalanuvchi hamda tarbiyachi, bolalar psixologiyasi, rivojlanish, ta'lim, tarbiya, innovatsion texnologiyalar.

Maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislari ta'lim tizimida innovatsion g'oyalarni yaratish va joriy etish zamonaviy bolalar bog'chasini rivojlantirish uchun zaruriy shartdir degan fikrga kelishib olishadi. Moliyalashtirish yuzasidan davlat muassasalari “Maktabgacha tarbiyachiga pul ketayotganda” innovatsion tashkiliy yechimlarining kundalik tartibida kiradigan innovatsion tashkiliy yechimlarning kunlik tartibiga kiritilishi institutning obro'sini sezilarli darajada oshiradi va rivojlanishning keyingi yo'nalishlarini belgilab beradi. O'quv jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish Psixofizik yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda, maktabgacha tarbiyachilar tomonidan har doim ijobiy seziladi, ular faoliyatni osongina o'zgartiradilar.

Maktabgacha yoshi - bu bolaning atrofida dunyoni faol o'rganadigan davr. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar o'zlarining psixologik rivojlanish xususiyatlariga ega. Yurish boshlaganida, bola juda ko'p kashfiyotlar qiladi, xonada, ko'chada, bolalar bog'chasida joylashgan narsalar bilan tanishadi. Turli narsalarni yig'ish, ularni o'rganish, mavzudan kelib chiqqan tovushlarni tinglash, bu ob'ektning qaysi fazilatlarini va xususiyatlarini borligini biladi. Ushbu davrda bolaning ingl. -figurativ va ingl. Effektiv fikrlash shakllari yaratilgan. 5-6 yoshligida bola shimgich kabi barcha ma'lumotlarni so'radi. Olimlar ushbu yoshlik davrida bolaning bu ma'lumotni esga olishini, bundan keyin u hayotda hech qachon eslamasligini isbotladi. Bola ufqlarini kengaytira oladigan har qanday narsaga qiziqish uyg'otadigan davrdir va bu uning atrofidagi dunyoni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. XXI asr texnika va texnologiyalar asri. Bu zamonda yangiliksiz, izlanishsiz, yaratuvchanliksiz inson mustaqil individ sifatida hayotda o'z o'rniga ega bo'lolmaydi. XXI asr texnika va texnologiyalar asri hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda har bir oilada texnik qurilmalar – masalan, mobil telefonlari, televizor, kompyuter, planshet va boshqalar kundalik iste'molda keng qo'llanadi. Shunisi diqqatga sazovorki, kichik yoshdagi bolalar kattalarga nisbatan bu qurilmalardan tez va oson foydalanishadi. Ammo, maqsadga yo'naltirilganlik darajasi juda oddiy. Shu ma'noda, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini to'liq texnologiyalar bilan ta'minlanish bosqichiga o'tilmoqda. Bu esa ta'limda ko'rgazmali qurollardan, zamonaviy texnologiyalar asosida foydalanish imkoniyatini kengaytiradi.

Xususan, yurtboshimiz Sh.Mirziyoyev maktabgacha ta'lim tizimi haqida quyidagi fikrlarni bejizga bildirmagan edilar: “Aslida, farzandlarimiz tarbiyasida eng asosiy bo'g'in hisoblangan maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining jamiyatimiz hayotidagi o'rni va ahamiyatini hech narsa bilan o'lchab bo'lmaydi. Aynan maktabgacha ta'lim sohasiga bo'lgan e'tibor mamlakatning ertangi taraqqiyoti uchun mustahkam zamin yaratadi”[1]. Maktabgacha ta'lim

tashkilotlarida tashkil etilayotgan mashg'ulotlarda qo'llanilayotgan interfaol usullar ta'lim samaradorligi hamda muhitini yaxshilaydi. Ta'lim innovatsiyasi deyilganda avvalo mashg'ulotlarda pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish nazarda tutiladi. Tarbiyachining kasbiy mahorati oshadi. Bolalar ijtimoiy muhitda, jamoasida o'z o'rnini his qila boshlaydi. Hozirgi kun talabi tez o'zgaruvchan, murakkab va o'zaro bir-biriga bog'liq dunyoda o'z o'rnini topa oladigan shaxsni tarbiyalashdir.

Kreativlik (lot ing. "sreate"–yaratish, "sreative" yaratuvchi ijodkor)–individning yangi g'oyalarni ishlab chiqarishga tayyorlikni tavsiflovchi hamda mustaqil omil sifatida iqtidorlikning tarkibiga kiruvchi ijodiy qobiliyati ma'nosini ifodalaydi Shaxsning kreativligi uning tafakkurida, muloqotida, his-tuyg'ularida, muayyan faoliyat turlarida namoyon bo'ladi. Kreativlik shaxsni yaxlit holda yoki uning muayyan xususiyatlarini, zehni o'tkirlikni tavsiflaydi. Shuningdek, kreativlik iqtidorning muhim omili sifatida aks etadi. Mutaxassislarining ta'kidlashicha, shtatlardagi innovatsion texnologiyalar nafaqat mumkin, balki ehtiyoj ham. Biroq, buni yodda tutish kerak pedagogik texnologiyalar maktabgacha bolalarning o'quv jarayonida qo'llanilishi mumkin, bir nechta qat'iy talablar berildi. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi:

Umuman olganda, maktabgacha yoshdagi yoshlar xotirjamlik hissi bilan ajralib turadi. Ularning kichik sabablarga ko'ra ziddiyatlari va kuchli affektiv epizootiyalari yo'q. Biroq, bu bolaning hissiy hayotining to'yinganligi pasayadi degani emas. Axir, preschooler kuni juda ko'p his-tuyg'ularga to'lib ketadi, shuning uchun kechqurun bola charchagan va to'liq charchash uchun keladi. Bu davrda hissiy jarayonlarning tuzilishi ham o'zgaradi. Ilgari motorli va vegetativ reaksiyalar maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda saqlanib qolgan emotsional jarayonlarga kiritilgan, ammo hissiyotlarning tashqi ifodasi yanada cheklangan shaklga ega bo'ladi. Maktab o'quvchilari nafaqat bugungi kunda qilayotgan ishidan, balki kelajakda nima qilishidan ham xafa bo'lib, xursand bo'lishadi. Presedrga tegishli bo'lgan har bir narsa - rasm, o'yin, qolib tuzish, onaga yordam berish, uy ishlarini bajarish - yorqin hissiy rangga ega bo'lishi kerak, aks holda narsalar tezda yiqilay yoki umuman bo'lmaydi. Chunki bu yoshdagi bola unga qiziq bo'lmagan ishni bajarolmaydi. Bu asrda, maktabgacha tarbiyachilarning boshqalarga va o'zlariga bo'lgan munosabati muhim ko'rsatkichdir. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar ko'pincha kamchiliklarini tanqid qilishadi, tengdoshlariga shaxsiy xususiyatlar beriladi, bolalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar, shuningdek, kattalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi munosabatni qayd qiladi. Biroq, ota-onalar bolalarga misol bo'la oladi. Shuning uchun, ota-onalar bolaga ijobiy ma'lumotni kiritish, shaxsiy yoki intellektual ma'lumot bo'lsin, u bolaga qo'rquv, xavotir va haqoratni keltirmasliklari kerak.

Shuningdek, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalar uchun alohida ingliz va rus tili xonalarini tashkil etish foydadan xoli emas. U yerda guruhlar navbat bilan mashg'ulot o'tkazishadi. Bolalar barcha innovatsion texnologiya vositalari, o'yinchoqlar, ko'rgazmalar vositasida mashg'ulot olib borsalar, jihozlarga ham shikast yetmaydi, nurlanishning oldi ham olinadi. Muhimi, bunday alohida xonalar bo'ylab yurish bolalarga yaxshi ta'sir qiladi. Ularda ana shunday xonalarga bo'lgan intilish darsga bo'lgan qiziqishning ortib borishiga sabab bo'ladi. Xonaga kirganda bolalar o'zlarini xuddi chet elga tushib qolgandek his qilishlari uchun xona devorlari ham aynan shunday beztiladi. O'yinchoqlar berilganda tarbiyachi har bir o'yinchoqning inglizcha nomini aytib asta sekinlik bilan bolalarga o'rgatishi kerak.

Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar jamiyat va mamalakat taraqqiyoti bilan jadal suratda rivojlanib boradi. Shunday ekan, endilikda juda katta doimiy ish o'rinlariga ega tsex hamda fabrikalar yonida kelajakda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlariga ehtiyoj paydo bo'ladi. Bunda uzoqroqda yashaydigan tarbiyalanuvchilarni olib keluvchi alohida avtobuslar tashkil qilish, bunday muassasalarning ish tartibi va dasturlari haqida fikr yuritish ham alohida

muammolardan hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy, innovatsion o‘qitish usullarini qo‘llash. Bunday usullar bolajak mutaxassisning kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishga, o‘quvchilarni faol bilim va amaliy faoliyatga jalb etishga, bilish jarayonida tashabbuskorlikni namoyon etishga yo‘naltirilgan bo‘lishi kerak. Ta‘lim dasturlarini passiv assimilyatsiya qilish istisno qilinadi.

Ta‘lim jarayonida zamonaviy infratuzilmaning mavjudligi. U o‘qitishning yangi shakl va usullarini, xususan, masofaviy ta‘limni qo‘llashga yordam beradigan axborot, texnologik, tashkiliy va kommunikatsiya komponentlariga asoslanishi kerak. Ta‘limda innovatsion texnologiyalar o‘qitishda muayyan yondashuvlarni qo‘llash asosida qo‘llaniladi, ya‘ni yangi texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish uchun asos bo‘lgan talablar va maqsadlarni o‘z ichiga olgan tamoyillar. Pedagogik sohadagi barcha innovatsiyalar jamiyat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishining hozirgi bosqichiga qat‘iy mos kelishiga asoslanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda ular o‘quvchilarning mustaqilligini rivojlantirishga, o‘z-o‘zini o‘rganish va o‘z-o‘zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirishga, o‘quv dasturlarini mexanik ravishda emas, balki ongli ravishda o‘zlashtirishga qaratilishi kerak. Mamlakatimizdagi deyarli barcha maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlari zamonaviy kompyuter va telekommunikatsiya texnologiyalari bilan jihozlangan. Bu esa, o‘z navbatida, tarbiyachilarning o‘z mehnat faoliyatlariga yangicha yondashuvlarini talab etadi. Ta‘lim jarayoniga yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etilishi, tarbiyachini texnik vositalar tomonidan siqib chiqishiga emas, balki yangicha yondashuv orqali uning vazifasi va rolini o‘zgartirib, tarbiyachilik faoliyatini yana-da serqirra, ijodiy va kreativ yondashuvga asoslangan kasbga aylantiradi.

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MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA OILAVIY HAMKORLIKNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlikning ahamiyati va uning bolaning rivojlanishidagi roli yoritilgan. Maqolada ota-ona va tarbiyachi o'rtasidagi samarali muloqot, oilaviy faoliyatni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish, uyda qo'llaniladigan metodlar, oilaning pedagogik jarayonga jalb etilishi hamda bolaning nutq, ijtimoiy va hissiy rivojlanishiga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy oilaviy hamkorlik yondashuvlari, interaktiv metodlar va individual yondashuv orqali bolalarning rivojlanishini ta'minlash masalalari ham ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oilaviy hamkorlik, ota-ona, tarbiyachi, maktabgacha ta'lim, nutq rivoji, ijtimoiy rivojlanish, hissiy rivojlanish, interaktiv metod, pedagogik yondashuv, bolalar rivoji;

Abstract: This article highlights the importance of family cooperation in preschool education and its role in a child's development. It analyzes effective communication between parents and educators, the integration of family activities into the educational process, home-based learning methods, and the family's involvement in the pedagogical environment. The study also explores how family engagement influences children's speech, social, and emotional development. Furthermore, the article discusses modern approaches to family cooperation, interactive methods, and individualized strategies that contribute to the holistic growth of preschool children.

Keywords: family cooperation, parents, educator, preschool education, speech development, social development, emotional development, interactive method, pedagogical approach, child development.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается значение семейного сотрудничества в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях и его роль в развитии ребёнка. Рассматриваются вопросы эффективного взаимодействия между родителями и воспитателями, интеграция семейной деятельности в образовательный процесс, методы, применяемые дома, а также влияние участия семьи в педагогическом процессе на развитие речи, социальных и эмоциональных качеств ребёнка. Кроме того, в статье анализируются современные подходы к семейному сотрудничеству, интерактивные методы и индивидуальные подходы, способствующие всестороннему развитию детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: семейное сотрудничество, родители, воспитатель, дошкольное образование, развитие речи, социальное развитие, эмоциональное развитие, интерактивный метод, педагогический подход, развитие ребёнка.

Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlik - bu bolaning shaxs sifatida shakllanishida eng muhim pedagogik yo'nalishlardan biridir. Ta'lim jarayonida oilaning faol ishtiroki bolaning ijtimoiylashuvi, o'ziga ishonch, mustaqillik va muloqot madaniyatining rivojlanishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Oila bola uchun birinchi tarbiya maktabi hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va oila o'rtasida muntazam, tizimli hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish tarbiyachining eng muhim vazifalaridan biri sanaladi [1]. Ota-onalar va tarbiyachilar o'rtasida o'zaro ishonchli muloqot o'rnatilsa, bola o'zini xavfsiz va qadrlangan his etadi, bu esa uning hissiy barqarorligini ta'minlaydi. Psixolog Vygotskiy [2] ta'kidlaganidek, bolaning rivojlanishida "yaqin rivojlanish zonasi" konsepsiyasi muhim ahamiyatga ega - ya'ni, bola kattalar bilan hamkorlikda o'z imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Shu

sababli, tarbiyachi va ota-onaning birgalikdagi faoliyati bolaning kognitiv, nutqiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi o‘rin tutadi.

Oilaviy hamkorlik turli shakllarda namoyon bo‘ladi: ota-onalar yig‘ilishlari, ochiq darslar, seminar-treninglar, oilaviy tanlovlar, “Ota-onalar kuni”, “Oila va bola” mavzusidagi suhbatlar va interaktiv uchrashuvlar. Bunday tadbirlar ota-onalarga ta‘lim-tarbiya jarayonining mohiyatini tushunish, bolalar bilan to‘g‘ri muloqot qilish, emotsional qo‘llab-quvvatlash va tarbiyaviy strategiyalarni to‘g‘ri tanlashda yordam beradi [2]. Masalan, “Ota-onalar ishtirokida ertak kuni” kabi tadbirlar nafaqat bolalarda kitobga qiziqishni, balki ota-ona bilan hissiy aloqani mustahkamlaydi. Ota-ona bolasi bilan birgalikda hikoya o‘qib, rollarni ijro etsa, bola o‘z fikrini erkin ifoda etishga, nutqni to‘g‘ri shakllantirishga o‘rganadi. Shu bilan birga, ota-onaning o‘zi ham ta‘lim jarayonining faol ishtirokchisiga aylanadi, bu esa pedagogik hamkorlikning barqaror tizimini yaratadi [3]. Oilaviy hamkorlikning yana bir muhim yo‘nalishi – kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishdir. Bolaning muloqot qilish madaniyati asosan oilada shakllanadi, shu bois tarbiyachilar ota-onalarga bola bilan muloqotning ijobiy usullarini o‘rgatishlari lozim. Ota-ona bolani tinglash, fikrini qadrlash, tanqid o‘rniga ijobiy rag‘bat berish orqali uning o‘ziga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi [2]. Ota-onaning mehri, izchil va rag‘batlantiruvchi so‘zlari bolada nutq rivoji bilan bir qatorda hissiy barqarorlikni ham shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy ta‘limda interaktiv oilaviy hamkorlik texnologiyalari keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Masalan, onlayn platformalarda ota-onalar uchun pedagogik treninglar, virtual maslahatlar, bolaning rivojlanish monitoringi va tarbiyachi-ota-ona guruh chatlari tashkil etiladi. Bu usullar orqali ota-onalar farzandining rivojlanishini doimiy kuzatib borish imkoniga ega bo‘ladilar va tarbiyachi bilan tezkor axborot almashadilar.

Shuningdek, oilaviy hamkorlik bolaning ijtimoiy ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda ham beqiyos ahamiyatga ega. Ota-onalar bilan birgalikdagi loyihalar, ekologik aksiyalar yoki “Oila va tabiat” mavzusidagi tadbirlar orqali bolalar jamoada ishlashni, tabiatni asrashni, ijtimoiy mas‘uliyatni his etishni o‘rganadilar [1]. Bu jarayonlar orqali bola o‘zini jamiyatning faol a‘zosi sifatida his etadi. Oilaviy hamkorlikni samarali yo‘lga qo‘yishda tarbiyachining roli beqiyosdir. U nafaqat ta‘lim jarayonini tashkil etadi, balki ota-onalarga pedagogik maslahat beradi, ularni bolaning psixologik holatidan xabardor qiladi, individual yondashuvni ta‘minlaydi va bolaning ijobiy rivojlanish dinamikasini kuzatib boradi [2]. Shu tariqa, oilaviy hamkorlik -bu nafaqat pedagogik jarayonning bir qismi, balki ta‘limning samaradorligini oshiruvchi ijtimoiy-madaniy tizimdir. U bolaning har tomonlama rivojlanishi, nutqiy kompetensiyasi, ijodkorligi va hissiy muvozanatini ta‘minlaydi. Ota-ona va tarbiyachi o‘rtasidagi doimiy hamkorlik bolani kelajakdagi ta‘lim bosqichlariga puxta tayyorlaydi, o‘qishga bo‘lgan motivatsiyasini oshiradi va o‘z-o‘zini rivojlantirishga turtki beradi.

Maktabgacha ta‘lim muassasalarida oilaviy hamkorlikni rivojlantirish -bu zamonaviy pedagogikaning eng muhim yo‘nalishlaridan biridir. Ota-ona va tarbiyachi o‘rtasida o‘zaro ishonch, hamjihatlik va muloqotning mavjudligi bolaning shaxsiy rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi omil bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Oila va ta‘lim muassasasi o‘rtasida uyg‘un hamkorlik bo‘lgandagina bola o‘zini xavfsiz, qadrlangan va muvaffaqiyatli his etadi. Shu sababli, maktabgacha ta‘lim tizimida ota-onalar uchun muntazam seminarlar, psixologik treninglar, interaktiv uchrashuvlar tashkil etish, bolalarning oilaviy faoliyatda ishtirokini rag‘batlantirish zarurdir. Bunday yondashuv bolada nafaqat bilim, balki ijtimoiy javobgarlik, mustaqillik va ijobiy hayotiy qadriyatlarni shakllantiradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA KITOB O‘QISHGA QIZIQISHNI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o‘qishga qiziqishni shakllantirish metodlari yoritilgan. Maqolada hikoya va ertaklar orqali bolalarda o‘qishga qiziqish uyg‘otish, interaktiv o‘qish mashg‘ulotlari, dramatik va rolli o‘yinlar orqali kitob bilan ishlash, shuningdek, kitob tanlash, vizual materiallardan foydalanish va tarbiyachining pedagogik roli tahlil qilinadi. Maqola, shuningdek, zamonaviy metodlar, individual yondashuv va interaktiv usullar orqali bolalarning nutqiy, ijodiy va muloqot ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalariga alohida e’tibor qaratadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kitob o‘qish, qiziqish, maktabgacha yosh, interaktiv o‘qish, hikoya, ertak, dramatik o‘yin, tarbiyachi, pedagogik metod, nutq rivoji.

Abstract: This article discusses methods for developing an interest in reading among preschool children. It analyzes how storytelling and fairy tales can inspire a love of reading, how interactive reading activities, dramatic and role-playing games encourage engagement with books, and how to select appropriate reading materials. The article also examines the use of visual aids and the educator’s pedagogical role. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of modern methods, individualized approaches, and interactive techniques in fostering children’s speech, creativity, and communication skills.

Keywords: reading, interest, preschool age, interactive reading, storytelling, fairy tale, dramatic play, educator, pedagogical method, speech development.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются методы формирования интереса к чтению у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируется, как рассказы и сказки могут пробудить у детей любовь к чтению, как интерактивные занятия по чтению, драматические и ролевые игры способствуют взаимодействию с книгой. Также рассматриваются вопросы выбора книг, использования наглядных материалов и педагогическая роль воспитателя. Особое внимание уделяется современным методам, индивидуальному подходу и интерактивным способам развития речевых, творческих и коммуникативных навыков детей.

Ключевые слова: чтение, интерес, дошкольный возраст, интерактивное чтение, рассказ, сказка, драматическая игра, воспитатель, педагогический метод, развитие речи.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o‘qishga qiziqish shakllantirish jarayoni bolaning tafakkurini, nutqini, tasavvurini, ijodiy fikrlash va muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lib, bu jarayonda tarbiyachi va pedagogik metodlar

asosiy rolni o'ynaydi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ertak va hikoyalarni interaktiv o'qish orqali bolalarda qiziqish uyg'onadi, ular kitob bilan mustaqil ishlashni o'rganadi, voqelikni tushunish va fikrini ifoda etish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi (Bosher, 2018, 34-b). Hikoyalarni dramatik va rolli o'yin shaklida o'qish bolalarda tafakkur, so'z boyligi va muloqot ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi, shuningdek, ularni voqelik bilan bog'lashni o'rgatadi (Vygotskiy, 1983, 96-b). Tarbiyachi kitob tanlashda bolalarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olib, qiziqarli, mavzuga mos hikoyalarni tanlashi, ular bilan dialog o'rnatishi, savol-javoblar va muammoli vaziyatlar orqali tafakkurini rivojlantirishi lozim [2]. Interaktiv o'qish mashg'ulotlari, masalan, "Rasm orqali hikoya tuzish", "Hikoya davomini aytish" yoki "Ertakni dramatik o'ynash" bolalarning so'z boyligini oshiradi, jumla tuzilishini mustahkamlaydi va ularni mavzu bo'yicha fikr almashishga rag'batlantiradi [3].

Shu bilan birga, multimediya vositalari, audio-kitoblar, video ertaklar va interaktiv kartochkalar bolalarning nutqiy faoliyatini faollashtiradi, ularni mustaqil fikrlashga, hikoya mazmunini tushunishga va yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirishga undaydi [1]. Tarbiyachi ushbu vositalardan foydalangan holda bolalarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olib individual yondashuvni tatbiq etadi va interaktiv mashg'ulotlar orqali ularni ijodiy fikrlash, muloqot va nutqiy kompetensiya ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi [1]. Shuningdek, hikoyalar va ertaklarni o'qish jarayonida tarbiyachi bolalarni mavzuga qiziqtirish uchun vizual materiallar, rasimli kartochkalar va dramatik sahnalar orqali qiziqarli faoliyat yaratadi. Masalan, ertak qahramonlarini rol o'ynash orqali bolalar voqealarni eslab qolish, ular haqida savol-javob berish va voqealarni o'z so'zlari bilan ifodalash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi [2]. Bu jarayon bolalarda ijodiy fikrlashni, mavzuni kengaytirish qobiliyatini, shuningdek, ijtimoiy va hissiy tajribani rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari, kitob tanlashda bolalar qiziqishi, ularning yosh va qobiliyat darajasi hisobga olinadi. Tarbiyachi hikoya yoki ertakni bolalarga tushunarli va qiziqarli shaklda taqdim etishi, ularni voqeani qayta so'zlashga, savollar berishga va muammoli vaziyatlarda fikr bildirishga rag'batlantirishi lozim [1].

Tarbiyachining individual yondashuvi, interaktiv metodlar va multimediya vositalarining uyg'unligi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kitob o'qishga qiziqish shakllantirish jarayonini samarali qiladi va bolalarni kelajakdagi ta'lim bosqichlariga tayyorlashda mustahkam poydevor yaratadi [1]. Shu tariqa, kitob o'qishga qiziqishni shakllantirish metodlari zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar, dramatik va interaktiv metodlar, multimedia vositalari hamda tarbiyachining individual yondashuvi orqali bolalarning nutqiy, ijodiy, intellektual va ijtimoiy rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA O'YIN TEXNOLOGIYALARINING AHAMIYATI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish jarayonida o‘yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Maqolada o‘yin faoliyati orqali bolalarning so‘z boyligini kengaytirish, to‘g‘ri talaffuzni shakllantirish, muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish hamda og‘zaki nutqni mustahkamlash yo‘llari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy o‘yin texnologiyalarining pedagogik samaradorligi, interaktiv yondashuvlarning ahamiyati, tarbiyachining roli va individual yondashuvlar orqali nutqiy rivojlanishni ta‘minlash masalalari ham ko‘rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: nutq rivoji, o‘yin texnologiyalari, og‘zaki muloqot, so‘z boyligi, talaffuz, kommunikativ kompetensiya, tarbiyachi, innovatsiya, interaktiv metod, ta‘lim texnologiyasi

Abstract: This article explores the importance of using play-based technologies in the development of speech among preschool-aged children. It analyzes how play activities can expand children’s vocabulary, shape correct pronunciation, enhance communication culture, and strengthen oral expression. Additionally, the article examines the pedagogical effectiveness of modern game technologies, the significance of interactive approaches, the role of educators, and the importance of individualized methods in ensuring speech development.

Keywords: speech development, play technologies, oral communication, vocabulary, pronunciation, communicative competence, educator, innovation, interactive method, educational technology.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение использования игровых технологий в процессе развития речи у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируются способы расширения словарного запаса, формирования правильного произношения, развития культуры общения и укрепления устной речи посредством игровой деятельности. Кроме того, в статье освещаются педагогическая эффективность современных игровых технологий, значение интерактивных подходов, роль воспитателя и индивидуальные методы, обеспечивающие речевое развитие детей.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи, игровые технологии, устное общение, словарный запас, произношение, коммуникативная компетенция, воспитатель, инновация, интерактивный метод, образовательные технологии.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayoni bolaning fikrlash, muloqot qilish va o‘z fikrini ifoda etish qobiliyatini shakllantirishning eng muhim bosqichi bo‘lib, bu jarayonda o‘yin texnologiyalari tabiiy, qiziqarli va samarali vosita sifatida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki o‘yin bolaning tafakkuri, e‘tiborini kuchaytiradi, so‘z boyligini kengaytiradi va og‘zaki nutqni shakllantiradi, shuningdek, bolalarni faol muloqotga jalb qiladi, ularni rolli va didaktik mashg‘ulotlar orqali ijtimoiy va hissiy tajriba bilan boyitadi, nutqdagi xatolarni erkin tuzatish, o‘z fikrini erkin ifoda etish va boshqa bolalar bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyatini beradi. Nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonida til o‘yinlari, dramatik mashg‘ulotlar va interaktiv o‘yin texnologiyalari asosiy vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi, ular bolalarda talaffuz, grammatik tuzilish va so‘z boyligini mustahkamlaydi, shuningdek, muammoli vaziyatlarda mustaqil qaror qabul qilish va ijodiy fikrlash ko‘nikmalarini shakllantiradi.

Shu tariqa, o‘yin texnologiyalari bolalarda nafaqat nutqiy kompetensiyani, balki mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash va ijtimoiy ko‘nikmalarni ham rivojlantiradi, bolaning o‘z

fikriga ishonchini mustahkamlaydi, yangilik yaratish istagini oshiradi va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish malakasini shakllantiradi, bu esa uning keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi uchun mustahkam poydevor yaratadi. Shu bilan birga, o'yin texnologiyalari bolaga ijtimoiy muhitda o'zini erkin ifoda etish, jamoaviy ishlarni bajarish va muloqot madaniyatini o'rganish imkonini beradi, bu esa bolaning nafaqat til kompetensiyasini, balki hissiy, ijtimoiy va intellektual rivojlanishini ham ta'minlaydi va kelajakdagi o'qish va ijtimoiy hayotga tayyorgarlikni mustahkamlaydi. O'yin texnologiyalari ta'lim jarayonini qiziqarli shaklda tashkil etish, bolaning bilimni amaliy faoliyat orqali mustahkamlash, nutqiy faoliyatga jalb qilish, yangi so'zlarni o'rgatish, to'g'ri talaffuz va grammatik qurilish bilan tanishtirishga imkon yaratadi, shuningdek, til o'yinlari, rolli o'yinlar, dramatik mashg'ulotlar va didaktik o'yinlar bolalarda nutqiy faollikni oshiradi, muloqotga tayyorlaydi va bolalarning mustaqil fikrlash, qaror qabul qilish va ijodiy yondashuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.

Tarbiyachi o'yin jarayonini boshqaruvchi, yo'naltiruvchi va rag'batlantiruvchi shaxs sifatida muhim o'rin tutadi, bolaning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda interaktiv va zamonaviy o'yin texnologiyalarini tatbiq etadi va bolalarning hissiy, ijtimoiy va nutqiy rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi. Shu tariqa, o'yin texnologiyalari bolalarda nafaqat nutqiy kompetensiyani, balki mantiqiy tafakkur, ijodiy fikrlash va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni ham rivojlantiradi, bolaning o'z fikriga ishonchini oshiradi, yangilik yaratish istagini rag'batlantiradi va uning keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi uchun mustahkam poydevor yaratadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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RAQAMLI TA'LIM VA GAMIFIKATSIYA USULLARINING CHET TILI O'QITISHDAGI SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli ta'lim vositalari va gamifikatsiya yondashuvlarining chet tili o'qitish jarayoniga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli o'yin elementlari o'quvchilar motivatsiyasini oshiradi, kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantiradi va o'rganish jarayonini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan shaklga keltiradi. Maqolada xalqaro tajriba hamda O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimidagi joriy etish istiqbollari yoritiladi.

Kerakli so'zlar: raqamli ta'lim, gamifikatsiya, chet tili ta'limi, innovatsion metodlar, o'quvchi motivatsiyasi, raqamli kompetensiya, interaktiv ta'lim, texnologiyalar, onlayn o'qitish, ta'lim sifati.

Bugungi texnologiyalar asrida hayotimizni gadjetlar,internet olami yoki elektr energiyasiz hayotimizni tassavur qilish qiyin.Gadjetlar bizni har tomondan qurshab olgan va hayotimizni ajralmas bo'lagiga aylangan.Shuningdek, bu shiddatli axborot asri avlodlari ziyrak va har jabhada faol,ular uchun yangicha yondashuv yangicha nazar zarur.Ayni shu masalada so'nggi yillarda har bir sohaga "raqamlashtirish" tushunchasi kirib keldi.Shubhasiz ta'lim sohasida bu masalada bajarilgan ishlar salmog'i ulkan.Binobarin,xorijiy til ta'limi jarayoni butnlay yangi ko'lam kasb etdi.Bu jarayonda ilg'or texnologiyalar,sun'iy intellekt tizimlari,interaktiv platformalar va gamifikatsiya elementlari orqali bu jarayonni yangi bosqichga ko'tarilmoqda so'nggi yillarda. 2020-yildan so'ng,ayniqsa pandemiya davrida butun jahon bo'ylab ta'lim onlayn formatga o'tkazildi.Bu esa sohani yanada ommalashishiga olib keldi, onlayn ta'lim vositalarining samaradorligi bo'yicha keng miqyosdagi tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi (OECD, 2022; Cambridge Assessment, 2023).

Raqamli muhitda o'qitish bu o'quvchi va o'qituvchiga nima beroladi?An'anaviy o'qitish tizimiga nisbatan qanday afzalliklari mavjud? So'nggi yillardagi aynan shu masalada olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki,raqamli muhitdagi ta'lim o'quvchini passiv bilim oluvchidan faol ishtirokchiga aylantiradi.Ta'lim jarayoni shaxsiylashadi oq'uvchi motivatsiyasi oshadi til o'rganishga nisbatan.Bu jarayonning eng samarali yondashuvlaridan biri — gamifikatsiya, ya'ni o'yin elementlarini o'qitish jarayoniga integratsiya qilishdir (Prensky, 2021).

Gamifikatsiya (ing. gamification) — o'yin mexanikasini ta'lim jarayoniga tatbiq etish bo'lib, u o'quvchilarning rag'batini oshirish, ijobiy raqobat muhitini yaratish va muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi (Dörnyei, 2020).

O'yin mexanikasi bu an'anaviy ta'lim ta'limdan ko'ra ko'proq natijalar beradi qachonki biz undan to'g'ri foydana olsak.Masalan,Kahoot va quizlet platformalarini olaylik men ularni o'z darslarimda qo'llashni boshlaganimda shuni angladimki,biz ulardan foydalanish orqali har qanday mavzu va yoshga to'g'ri keladigan qiziqarli dars yarata olamiz.Xususan bolalar va telefon o'yinlariga bo'g'lanib qolgan bolalar bilan ishlashda bu sizga yaxshi ko'makchi. Bu masalada natijalarga yuzlansak,Son (2022) tomonidan Janubiy Koreyada o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda Quizizz va Kahoot platformalaridan foydalanish o'quvchilarning darsdagi ishtirokini 38% ga oshirgan, motivatsiya darajasi esa 27% ga ko'tarilgan. Avvalgi dars jarayoni zerikarli tuyilgan bo'lsa,keyinchalik bolalar "Yana o'yin o'ynaylik"deb so'rashni boshlashadi.Biz uchun o'qitishning bir qismi bo'lgan bu tizim ular uchun qiziqarli o'yinga aylanadi.

Shu o'rinda barchamiz uchun qadrdonga aylangan Duolingo ilovasi haqida,ilova o'zida 40 dan ortiq tillar uchun kurslarni saqlaydi.O'yinlashgan tizim(ball,daraja, mokufotlar),qisqa va soda mashqlarni o'zida jam qilgan va bu o'qish tizimini nafaqat qiziqarli sodda,doimiy va bosimlarsiz amalga oshiradi.O'rganuvchi o'rtacha 15-30 minut davomida shug'illanadi va darslar qoldirilgan taqdirda,ilova foydalnuvchiga bu haqida bildirishnoma jo'natadi va yana o'rganish jarayoniga qaytaradi.Oxford University Press (2023) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, Duolingo singari mobil ilovalar orqali o'qigan o'quvchilarda so'z boyligi o'sishi 1,7 barobar yuqori bo'lgani kuzatilgan.

Evropaning 12 ta universitetida o'tkazilgan meta-tahlil (de Freitas et al., 2024) davomida gamifikatsiya qilingan ta'limda o'rganish natijasi an'anaviy metoddagi ta'limga nisbatan o'rtacha 23% samaraliroq ekanligini ko'rsatgan.

Quyidagi platformalar haqidagi tadqiqotlarda erishilgan natijalar bilan bo'lishaman:

Kahoot So'z boyligini oshirish **25%** tezroq o'zlashtirish (Lee, 2022)

Quizizz Grammatik ko'nikmalar Xatoliklar **30%** kamaygan (Suryani, 2023)

Wordwall Vizual eslab qolish **40%** yaxshilanish (Aguirre, 2021)

Duolingo Mustaqil o'rganish O'rganish davomiyligi **2 baravar** uzaygan (Pérez, 2024)

Blooket Raqobat orqali motivatsiya 90% o'quvchilar "ko'proq qatnashishni" istagan (Johnson, 2023)

Shuningdek bu masalada yurtimizda olib borilayotgan ishlar miqyosi haqida O'zbekistonda "Raqamli ta'lim – 2030" strategiyasi doirasida maktablarda ingliz tili o'qitish bo'yicha bir qator raqamli loyihalar yo'lga qo'yildi (XTV, 2023). Ayni paytda MyELT, UzEDU va British Council platformalari o'quv jarayoniga joriy etilmoqda. Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda interfaol onlayn platformalar, video-darslar, virtual laboratoriyalar, til almashish (language exchange) va audio-video resurslardan foydalanish kengayishi. Shuningdek strategiyada "digital education resources" va "online education platforms"ni keng tatbiq etish ko'zda tutilgan.

Ammo bu yo'nalishda ko'pchiligimiz yo'l qo'yadigan xatolar mavjud gamifikatsiyani dars jarayonida qo'llashda. O'tkazilgan tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, aksariyat o'qituvchilar gamifikatsiya vositalarini faqat test uchun o'tilgan mavzuni mustahkamlash va imtihon qilish uchungina ishlatadi, lekin ular o'yin asosidagi o'rganish jarayonining metodik kuchini to'liq anglab yetmaydi. (Baxshieva, 2024).

Demak, avvalo o'qituvchilarni raqamli pedagogika bilan yaxshi tanishtirish kompetensiyasi bilan ta'minlash, ularni interaktiv vositalarni dars rejasiga integratsiya qilish bo'yicha tayyorlash zarur.

O'zinning tajribamda (5–6-sinf o'quvchilari bilan ishlashda), Kahoot va Wordwall dan foydalanish darsda jonlilik va musobaqa muhitini yaratadi. Har bir o'quvchi o'z natijasini ko'rib, tahlil qila olgani uchun o'ziga javobgarlik hissi va ishonchi oshadi. Eng muhimi, o'yin orqali o'rganish jarayonida ularni "ingliz tilini o'rganish kerak" degan majburiyatli bosimdan "o'ynab bilish" bosqichiga olib chiqadi.

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CHET TILLARNI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT TEKNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida axborot texnologiyalarining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati yoritilgan. Maqolada zamonaviy texnologiyalar — kompyuter dasturlari, interaktiv platformalar, multimedia vositalari va onlayn resurslardan foydalanish orqali o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, axborot texnologiyalarining o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, motivatsiyasini kuchaytirish hamda darslarni qiziqarli va interaktiv shaklda tashkil etishdagi afzalliklari ko'rsatib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Inavatsion texnologiyalar, axborot texnologiyalari, chet tili, ingliz tili, kompyuter, multimedia, oynayi jahon, audio.

Bugungi kunda dunyo har kuni, har bir soniyalarda rivojlanib bormoqda. Axborot texnologiyalar inson hayotiga katta ta'sir o'tqazmoqda. Bu jarayon hatto, ta'limda ham o'z ta'sirini sezdirmay qolmadi. Shuningdek, chet tilni o'rganish ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, axborot texnologiyalarda bir muncha yengillik kasb etmoqda. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, axborot texnologiyalari ta'lim sohasi bilan chambarchas bog'landi. O'zbekiston respublikasi prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich raisligida chet tillarni o'qitish tizimini takomillashtirishga bag'ishlangan selektorda chet tili o'qituvchilarga milliy va xalqaro sertifikatga ega bo'lish talabi ta'kidlandi. Hozirgi kunda kelib esa nafaqat chet tili balki, zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda dars mashg'ulotlarini olib borish ustuvor vazifalardan biriga aylangan.

Til o'rganish va o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning roli beqiyosdir. Texnologik vositalardan foydalanish chet tilning o'rganishning har bir aspect yani tinglab tushunish, yozish, o'qish va gapirishda qo'l keladi. Masalan, tinglab tushunish uchun, albatta kompyuter, pleyer, CD diskarsiz bu jarayonni amalga oshirib bo'lmaydi. Tinglab tushunish til o'rganishning eng muhim qismlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchi zamonaviy texnologiyalarni yaxshi o'zlashtirgan va ulardan foydalana olishni bilishi zarur. Bu jarayonda, jumladan:

-kompyuterlardan foydalanganda o'quvchi chet tilidagi video roliklarni, namoyishlarni, dialoglarni, kino yoki multfilimlarni ham ko'rishni va eshitib tushinishi mumkin;
-chet tillardagi radio eshitishlar va televidienadagi dasturlarni tomosha qilish mumkin;
-ancha an'anaviy usul hisoblangan magnitafon va kasetalardan foydalanish.

Bu texnik vositalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning chet tilini o'zgarishlari jarayonini qiziqarliroq va samaraliroq bo'lishini ta'millaydi.

Hozir chet tillarini o'rganishga yordam beradigan muhim, samarali va zamonaviy ilovalarni ko'rib chiqamiz. Turli xil ilovalardan foydalanib ko'plab, jumladan, ingliz, arab, ispan, fransuz, italyan, nemis, irland, golland, rus, xittoy va boshqa tillarni o'rganishingiz mumkin.

Duolingo ilovasi- bugungi kunda 9.6 million aktiv foydalanuvchilarga ega eng mashhur va keng qo'llaniladigan ilova hisoblanadi. Ilova orqali til o'rganishni boshlash jarayoni muvaffaqiyatli tarzda amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Shunchaki ilovani ochib, o'rganmoqchi bo'lgan tilingizni tanlaysiz va siz uchun alohida dars boshlanadi. Akkaunt ochib o'tirishingiz shart emas, lekin akkaunt yaratsangiz, ko'plab imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lasiz. Misol uchun, o'rganayotgan paytingizda, jarayonini saqlash va kuzatib borishingiz mumkin bo'ladi. Barcha darajadagi o'rganuvchilar: beginner, intermediate, advanced va

boshqalar foydalanish imkoniyatlariga ega. Mavzular turli xil mavzularga moslab chiqilgan. O‘qish, yozish, tinglab tushunish, so‘zlashish va shukabilarni barchasi uchun mashqlar mavjud. Kuningizning istalgan vaqtida va istalgan muddatda foydalana olasiz. Har bir bajarilgan mashqdan so‘ng harakatlanuvchi odamcha shaklidagi animatsiyalar foydalanuvchiga o‘ziga xos animatsiya beradi. Misol tariqasida, agarda siz mashqlarni yaxshi, a’lo darajada bajarsangiz animatsion odamchalar harakatlanib sizga tabassum qiladi va zo‘r deb ishora ko‘rsatadi. O‘rganish mumkin bo‘lgan tillar bular: ispan, fransuz, ingliz, nemis, xitoy, yapon, koreys, italyan, portugal, golland, irland, shved, turk, norveg, ukrain, rus, polyak, hind, vietnam, venger, grek, indonez, chex. Duolingo onlayn yoki Android, iOS va Windows uchun ilovalar orqali foydalanish mumkin.

FluentU- ushbu ilova orqali dunyo bo‘yicha eng ko‘p tarqalgan tillardagi video suhbatlarni subtitrl bilan ko‘rish imkoniyatlariga ega. Bu ilova ko‘rib o‘rganish qobiliyati “Audio-visual learners” kuchli o‘rganuvchilar uchun o‘z qulayliklariga ega. Buni afzalliklari: mavzular doirasi juda keng. Turli reklamalar ulardagi musiqalar va videolarni, suhbatlarni tinglash mumkin. Video ko‘rish davomida so‘zlarning subtitrl chiqib turadi va tushunishda qandaydir muammoga duch kelsangiz, ana shu so‘zni ustiga bosilsa, so‘z ma’nosini osongina topib olish imkoniyatlari mavjud.

Ibrat academy- bu ham bepul ilovalardan biri sanaladi. Ro‘yxatdan o‘tish orqali turli xil tillarni bepul va samarali usulda, tajribali ustozlardan o‘rganish mumkin. Dastur Android va iOS qurilmalarda mavjud. Loyiha orqali 30 dan ortiq kurslar taklif etilgan. Platformada ko‘plab foydalanuvchilar bo‘lib, sertifikat olganlar ham bor. Afzalliklari :Bepul — foydalanuvchilar uchun kurslar va darslar odatda bepul taklif qilinadi. Interaktiv o‘qish — viktorinalar, testlar, interaktiv mashqlar bilan ta’lim jarayoni jonli bo‘lishi kutiladi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, bugungi kunda texnikasiz hech bir ishni udallay olish qiyin hatto, ta’lim sohalarida ham. Informatika, raqamli texnologiyalar fanlari ham chet tillarni va fanlarni o‘qitish metodikasi bilan bog‘landi. O‘ylaymanki, endilikda axborot texnologiyalari orqali masofaviy hujjatlarni, turli kitob, jurnallarni, ta’lim doirasida ham qiyinchiliklar yuz bermaydi. Zero, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, axborot texnologiyalari chet tillarni mukammal egallash ilm cho‘qqisiga chiqish uchun manfaatli yo‘llardan biri bo‘lib hisoblanadi.

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ONA TILI – MILLAT G‘URURI: O‘ZBEK TILINING O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek tili, ya’ni ona tilining jamiyatdagi o‘rni va ahamiyati, shuningdek, yoshlar orasida tilga bo‘lgan hurmatning pasayishiga sabab bo‘layotgan omillar tahlil qilingan. Tilni asrash, uning nufuzini oshirish hamda yosh avlod ongida ona tiliga muhabbat uyg‘otish yo‘llari haqida ilmiy mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: o‘zbek, til, jamiyat, qadriyat, millat, jahon, davlat, ahamiyat, qisqartma.

Til – bu millatning ma’naviy asosini tashkil etuvchi eng muhim qadriyatlardan biridir. Ona tili har bir xalqning o‘zligini belgilovchi, uning madaniy, ijtimoiy va siyosiy hayotining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. O‘zbekiston Respublikasida o‘zbek tili davlat tili sifatida e’tirof etilib, jamiyat hayotining barcha jabhalarida faol qo‘llanilmoqda. Shunga qaramay, globalizatsiya, axborot texnologiyalari va xorijiy tillarning keng tarqalishi fonida ona tiliga bo‘lgan munosabatda muayyan o‘zgarishlar yuz bermoqda. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek tilining jamiyatdagi o‘rni, uning milliy o‘zlikni shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati hamda tilni asrash va rivojlantirish zarurati tahlil qilinadi.

O‘zbek tili tarixan boy, qadimiy va jahon tillari orasida o‘z o‘rniga ega til sifatida shakllangan. Mustaqillik yillarida tilimizning mavqei mustahkamlanib, uni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha qator davlat dasturlari amalga oshirildi. 1989-yil 21-oktabrda qabul qilingan “Davlat tili haqida”gi qonun esa o‘zbek tilining rasmiy maqomini huquqiy jihatdan mustahkamlab berdi. Shu sanadan boshlab har yili 21-oktabr kuni O‘zbek tili bayrami sifatida keng nishonlanadi.

Biroq, bugungi kunda axborot texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning keng tarqalishi natijasida yoshlar orasida so‘zlashuv tili o‘zgarib bormoqda. Ko‘plab yoshlar o‘zbek tilida gaplashganda inglizcha yoki ruscha so‘zlarni aralashtirib ishlatishadi. Masalan, “meeting”, “deadline”, “presentation” kabi so‘zlarning o‘rniga o‘zbekcha muqobillarini ishlatish unutilmoqda. Bu holat tilning sof shaklida qo‘llanilishiga putur yetkazadi va asta-sekin adabiy til me’yorlarining buzilishiga olib keladi. Til madaniyatini pasaytirayotgan yana bir muhim omil – ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda qisqartma so‘zlar va noto‘g‘ri imlo bilan yozish odatidir. “Salom” o‘rniga “slm”, “boraman” o‘rniga “brm” kabi yozish holatlari tilning qadriyat sifatidagi mavqeini pasaytiradi. Bunday yozishmalar, ayniqsa, yoshlar orasida norma sifatida qabul qilinmoqda, bu esa yozma madaniyatning yemirilishiga sabab bo‘lmoqda.

Tilni asrash uchun zamonaviy, samarali va yoshlar uchun jozibali usullarni qo‘llash muhim. Masalan, ona tili bo‘yicha mobil ilovalar ishlab chiqish, unda noto‘g‘ri so‘zlarni avtomatik tuzatish, adabiy til me’yorlarini o‘rgatish tizimlarini yaratish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, “Ona tili challenge” kabi ijtimoiy tarmoq aksiyalari orqali yoshlarni ona tilida maqol, matal, she’r o‘qishga, so‘z boyligini namoyish etishga undash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bu nafaqat tilga hurmatni oshiradi, balki milliy g‘ururni rivojlantirishga ham xizmat qiladi.

Til – millatning g‘ururi, milliy o‘zlikning ifodasidir. Har bir inson o‘z tilini qadrlab, unga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo‘lsa, jamiyatda milliy birlik va ma’naviyat mustahkamlanadi. Taniqli adiblar ta’kidlaganidek, 'til yo‘qolgan millat – yo‘qolgan xalqdir'. Shu bois, ona tiliga e’tibor berish, uni to‘g‘ri, ravon va adabiy me’yorda ishlatish har bir fuqaroning burchidir.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o‘zbek tili – bu xalqning ko‘zgusi, millatning g‘ururi va ajralmas boyligidir. Ona tilini rivojlantirish, uni yoshlar orasida ommalashtirish, sofligini saqlash va xalqaro miqyosda tanitish bugungi kunning muhim vazifalaridan biridir. Har bir fuqaro o‘z ona tiliga sadoqat bilan qarasa, uning nufuzi, jozibasi va kuchi yanada ortadi. O‘zbek tili dunyo tillari orasida munosib o‘ringa ega bo‘lishi uchun uni amaliyotda faol ishlatish va ilmiy-texnik sohalarda ham rivojlantirish zarur.

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SUN’IY INTELEKTNING INGLIZ TILINI O‘RGANISHDAGI O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola orqali sun’iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalarining ingliz tilini o‘rganishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada zamonaviy ta’limda SI vositalaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari, ularning o‘quvchilarga ko‘rsatgan ijobiy ta’siri hamda ayrim salbiy jihatlari yoritib beriladi, shuningdek, sun’iy intellekt asosida ishlab chiqilgan ilovalar misolida ingliz tili o‘qitishning yangi metodlari ham tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Sun’iy intellekt, ingliz tili, ta’lim, texnologiya, interaktiv o‘rganish, raqamli ta’lim.

Hozirgi globallashuv jarayonida ta’lim tizimi boshqa sohalarga nisbatan jadallik bilan rivojlanmoqda. Ayniqsa, sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalarining paydo bo‘lishi o‘quv jarayonini tubdan o‘zgartirmoqda. Ingliz tili bugungi kunda xalqaro aloqa, biznes, fan va madaniyat tili sifatida e’tirof etilgan bo‘lib, uni o‘rganish barcha yoshlar va kattalar uchun ham anchagina samarali bo‘lib bormoqda. Buning natijasida bu tilni o‘rganishda yangi metodlar zarurati paydo bo‘lmoqda.

Shu nuqtai nazardan, sun’iy intellekt asosidagi dasturlar ingliz tili o‘qitishning eng samarali vositalaridan biriga aylanib bormoqda. Maqolaning maqsadi - sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ingliz tilini o‘rganishdagi o‘rni, afzalliklari va kamchiliklarini tahlil qilish hamda bu vositalarning ta’lim tizimidagi yutuqlarini yoritishdir.

Sun’iy intellekt - bu inson aql-idroki faoliyatini taqlid qiluvchi dasturiy tizimdir. U o‘rganish, tahlil qilish va qaror qabul qilish imkoniyatiga ega. Ta’lim sohasida AI texnologiyalari o‘quvchilarning bilim darajasini aniqlash, individual dars rejalarini tuzish, grammatik xatolarni avtomatik tuzatish va talaffuzni yaxshilashda keng qo‘llanmoqda. Bunday turdagi zamonaviy texnologiyalar asosida hattoki yoshlar ham mustaqil muvaffaqiyatlarga erishmoqda. Masalan, Duolingo, Grammarly, ChatGPT, Elsa Speak kabi platformalar o‘quvchilarga ingliz tilini mustaqil o‘rganishda katta yordam bermoqda. Bu dasturlar o‘quvchining bilim darajasiga mos mashqlarni taklif qiladi va natijalarni avtomatik tahlil qiladi. Hozirda bunday ilovalarga talab oshib bormoqda, negaki hamma uyda o‘tirgan holatda internet platformalaridan o‘zlariga tegishli ma’lumotlar va bilimlarni olishyapti. Hozirgi zamon talabidan kelib chiqib yondashadigan bo‘lsak, sun’iy intellektning hayotimiz davomida bir qancha afzallik tomonlari bor. Ularni bir nechta taqdim etishim mumkin.

Birinchiidan, AI individual yondashuvni ta'minlaydi. Har bir o'quvchining xatolarini, kuchli va zaif tomonlarini, va aynan qanday soha ularga mos yoki mos emasligini bolaning fikrlashi yoki qobiliyatiga qarab aniqlab, shunga mos o'quv material va ularni yoshiga mos metodikalar orqali ma'lumot beradi. Ikkinchiidan, AI real muloqot muhitini yaratadi. Masalan, ChatGPT kabi tizimlar orqali o'quvchilar ingliz tilida suhbatlashish, yozish va fikr bildirish mashqlarini bajarishlari mumkin. Buni qulay taraflaridan biri mashqlardagi xatolarini tez aniqlashi va muhim maslahatlarni berishida. Uchinchiidan, motivatsiya va qiziqishni oshiradi. O'quvchilar interaktiv topshiriqlar, ovozli testlar va gamifikatsiya elementlari orqali tilni zavq bilan o'rganadilar. Bunday metodika maktablarda ham ko'p qo'llaniladi. Masalan, o'quvchilarni darsdan zerikishini oldini olish uchun dars mobaynida turli xil o'yinlar va bolalarni rag'batlantirish, ularni o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini orttirish uchun turli sovg'a va kartochkalar berishadi.

To'rtinchiidan, AI o'qituvchilarga yordamchi vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. U dars rejalashtirish, baholash va tahlil jarayonlarini avtomatlashtiradi, bu esa o'qituvchiga ko'proq vaqtni o'quvchilarga bag'ishlash imkonini beradi. Albatta har narsaning ham ikkinchi tomoni bo'lgani kabi bunday texnologiyalarning ham afzalliklari bilan birga kamchiliklari ham yo'q emas. Jumladan: - o'quvchilar sun'iy intellektga haddan ortiq tayanib, mustaqil fikrlash va ijodkorlik ko'nikmalarini yo'qotish xavfi mavjud. Chunki hozirgi kunda Chatgpt judayam ommalashib ketgan va undan xohlagan mavzuda malumot olishingiz mumkin. Qanday turdagi savol bulishidan qat'iy nazar hammasini aniq faktlar bilan izohlab bera oladi. - ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi masalasi dolzarbdir. Ba'zi AI ilovalari foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini saqlab, tahlil qiladi. Bu judayam dolzarb masalaga aylanib bormoqda, sababi dunyo ahlosining ko'p qismi sun'iy intellektni foydalanuvchisiga aylanib ulgurgan, ammo mutaxassislarning ta'kidlashicha sun'iy intellekt vaqti kelib insonni shaxsiy ma'lumotlaridan o'ziga qarshi foydalanishi mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, sun'iy intellekt ingliz tilini o'rganishda zamonaviy, interaktiv va samarali vosita sifatida katta imkoniyatlarni taqdim etmoqda. U o'quvchilarga mustaqil o'rganish, xatolarni tahlil qilish va real muloqot muhitida tilni amaliy qo'llash imkonini beradi. Biroq, bu texnologiyalardan foydalanishda muvozanatni saqlash muhim - sun'iy intellekt o'qituvchini emas, balki o'rganish jarayonini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi vosita sifatida qaralishi lozim. Va undan foydalanuvchi har bir kishi o'zini aniq maqsadini bilib usha yo'nalishdagina foydalanishi kerak. Sun'iy intellekt bu bizga ilm olishning samaraliroq yo'lini ochib beruvchi vosita, bizni vazifalarimizni bajarib beruvchi emas. Bundan tashqari, kelajakda AI asosidagi ta'lim platformalarini milliy ta'lim tizimiga moslashtirish orqali ingliz tili o'qitish sifatini yanada oshirish imkoni ham yo'q emas.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE (L1) DURING THE ACQUISITION OF A SECOND LANGUAGE (L2)

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Abstract: Proficiency in foreign languages is a crucial component of both professional and personal competency in today's environment. However, the influence of the original

language (L1), which shows up as common learner errors at different language levels, frequently complicates the process of acquiring a second language (L2). In linguistics and instructional strategies, this effect is referred to as interference (or negative language transmission). Studying this issue is especially crucial since knowing how L1 interference works might improve methodological methods and boost the efficacy of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: language transfer, interference, native language (L1) influence, target language (L2) acquisition, contrastive linguistics.

First thoroughly studied in the middle of the 20th century within the framework of contrastive linguistics (R. Lado, 1957), the impact of the native language on learning a foreign language was later expanded upon in works on error analysis (S. Corder, 1967) and theories of interlanguage by L. Selinker (1972). The transfer of L1 elements can take the form of both positive transfer, which helps learners acquire similar structures, and negative transfer, which impedes the development of proper speech abilities, according to recent research in applied and pedagogical linguistics.

Learning a foreign language is always accompanied by the interaction of two language systems—the native (L1) and the target (L2). During acquisition, this interaction may have both beneficial and detrimental effects. "Language transfer" describes how learning a new language is impacted by learning a previously learned language. In the theory of second language acquisition (SLA), this idea is crucial.

Therefore, interference is a sign of the detrimental effects of the native language, manifested as grammatical, syntactic, vocabulary, or pronunciation mistakes. One common instance of interference is when Russian-speaking learners insert their native word order into English sentences, such as "He very likes coffee" rather than "He likes coffee very much."

In the middle of the 20th century, language transmission was first studied as a scientific phenomenon. The Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis (CAH), first forward by Robert Lado in 1957, was among the earliest theories of systems. This hypothesis states that the discrepancies between L1 and L2 can be used to anticipate difficulties in second language acquisition: the more differences there are, the higher the likelihood of errors.

However, it later became clear that not all learners' errors can be explained by the influence of the L1. Stephen Corder put forth the theory in 1967 that mistakes are a reflection of the learner's internal system and a normal aspect of language acquisition. Larry Selinker's interlanguage theory (1972) expanded on his methodology. This theory holds that the learner's second language system is an intermediate, dynamic system that combines aspects of the target and native languages rather than being a replica of the L2. Interference is therefore seen as a normal step in the development of an interlanguage rather than just a cause of mistakes. It demonstrates how a student reorganizes prior information in order to become proficient in a new language system. Interference can manifest itself at various levels of the language system. The most common forms are:

The transmission of L1 speech's articulatory and intonatory characteristics into L2 speech is known as phonetic interference. For instance, Russian-speaking learners may pronounce the English sound [θ] as [s] or [t] (think → sink). Using fictitious translators' pals and calques of terms (magazine "магазин," take decision instead of make a decision) is known as lexical interference. Errors resulting from variations in grammatical structures, like the inappropriate use of tenses or the absence of articles, are known as grammatical interference.

The transfer of word order and syntactic patterns from L1 is known as syntactic interference. A breach of speaking behavior, professionalism, directness, and other norms

caused on by cultural variations is known as pragmatic interference. It should be mentioned that interference can happen in written as well as oral communication, particularly when translating or writing in a foreign language.

Modern research in foreign language teaching methods shows that interference is not only a source of errors but also an important indicator of language acquisition progress. From the standpoint of the instructor, recognizing common signs of L1 interference enables the forecasting of possible challenges and the modification of instructional strategies. The Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis's contrastive approach is still applicable today, but it is now seen as a component of a broader strategy rather than as a stand-alone technique. Contemporary teaching methods include use of metalinguistic commentary, which enables students to actively examine their mistakes, and contrastive activities, which are designed to raise awareness of the distinctions between L1 and L2.

Effective use of cross-linguistic transfer data not only helps reduce the frequency of errors but also increases student motivation, as it makes the learning process more meaningful and predictable. Therefore, the teacher's job is to control and guide this process in a positive way rather than to totally eradicate the effect of the mother language. Interim conclusion: Interference with native language is a normal and unavoidable phase of learning a foreign language. The cognitive processes involved in moving information and abilities from one linguistic system to another are intimately related to it. Making thoughtful use of data on L1 interference manifestations helps educators create more effective teaching strategies based on learners' metacognition and comparison analysis.

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КРЕАТИВНЫЕ ВИДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ШКОЛАХ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются креативные формы обучения русскому языку в школьной практике. Актуальность темы обусловлена необходимостью

повышения мотивации учащихся и эффективности преподавания в условиях цифровизации образования и изменения когнитивных стратегий восприятия информации. Особое внимание уделяется таким методам, как игровые технологии, сторителлинг, проектная деятельность, использование цифровых ресурсов и междисциплинарная интеграция. Автор анализирует педагогические преимущества каждого подхода, иллюстрирует их примерами и подчеркивает значимость формирования языковой личности школьника средствами креативного обучения. Работа может быть полезна как практикующим педагогам, так и студентам педагогических специальностей.

Ключевые слова: русский язык, креативное обучение, школьное образование, игровые технологии, сторителлинг, цифровые ресурсы, проектная деятельность, мотивация учащихся, методика преподавания.

Annotation. The article examines the creative forms of teaching Russian language in school practice. The relevance of the topic is due to the need to increase students' motivation and teaching effectiveness in the context of digitalization of education and the change in cognitive strategies for information perception. Special attention is paid to such methods as game technologies, storytelling, project activities, the use of digital resources, and interdisciplinary integration. The author analyzes the pedagogical advantages of each approach, illustrates them with examples, and emphasizes the importance of forming a schoolchild's linguistic personality through creative learning. The work can be useful for both practicing teachers and students of pedagogical specialties.

Keywords: Russian language, creative learning, school education, game technologies, storytelling, digital resources, project activities, student motivation, teaching methodology.

Введение. Современная система школьного образования требует переосмысления традиционных методов преподавания русского языка. В условиях стремительного развития технологий, клипового мышления и снижения интереса учеников к академическим дисциплинам особую актуальность приобретает внедрение креативных подходов к обучению. Цель данной статьи - рассмотреть основные формы креативного преподавания русского языка в школе, их эффективность и методическое обоснование.

Русский язык как учебная дисциплина играет ключевую роль в формировании общей языковой и культурной компетенции школьников. Однако на фоне стремительных изменений в обществе и появлении новых образовательных запросов всё более остро встаёт вопрос о пересмотре традиционных методов преподавания. Ученики XXI века - это дети цифровой эпохи, обладающие клиповым мышлением, высоким уровнем визуального восприятия и сниженной концентрацией внимания. В связи с этим необходим поиск эффективных, нетрадиционных форм обучения, которые соответствовали бы актуальным потребностям школьников и формировали бы у них устойчивую мотивацию к изучению родного языка.

Креативные виды обучения - это не просто набор нестандартных приёмов, а целая система, направленная на развитие языковой личности школьника. Такие методы активизируют познавательную деятельность, развивают креативное и критическое мышление, способствуют более прочному усвоению материала. Использование сторителлинга, игровых технологий, мультимедийных ресурсов, проектной деятельности и междисциплинарной интеграции позволяет учителю выйти за рамки шаблонного урока и превратить обучение в живой, увлекательный процесс.

Цель этой статьи направлена на всесторонний анализ креативных подходов в обучении русскому языку в школьной практике. Рассматриваются их методологическая

основа, практические примеры внедрения и возможные результаты в контексте формирования языковой компетенции школьников

Обзор литературы. Для теоретического обоснования статьи использованы труды современных педагогов и методистов. Г.К.Селевко рассматривает креативные технологии как средство активизации учебного процесса. Л.Н.Смирнова акцентирует внимание на игровых формах обучения, способствующих формированию интереса к предмету. В работе Н.П.Копцевой освещены возможности цифровых ресурсов, повышающих эффективность усвоения материала. Сторителлинг как метод развития письменной речи анализируется Н.А.Пахомовой, А.М.Воронкова рассматривает проектную деятельность как способ формирования мотивации. И.Ю.Матвеева подчёркивает значимость межпредметных связей в обучении языку.

Методологической основой данной статьи являются принципы компетентностного и личностно-ориентированного подходов, а также идеи креативной педагогики. В исследовании использованы описательный и аналитический методы, позволяющие обобщить и систематизировать современные креативные практики преподавания русского языка в школе. Применялись также сравнительно-сопоставительный метод для анализа различных форм и методов обучения, а также метод педагогического моделирования - при описании возможных сценариев уроков с использованием креативных технологий.

Основным источником эмпирических данных послужили опубликованные педагогические разработки, методические рекомендации и примеры успешного внедрения нестандартных форм обучения в школьной практике. Такой подход позволил сделать выводы о потенциальной эффективности креативных методов в обучении русскому языку.

Анализ и результаты. Креативность в педагогике трактуется как способность к созданию нового педагогического продукта, приемов или стратегий, направленных на повышение мотивации и качества усвоения материала. Креативные методы преподавания предполагают отход от стандартизированных форм, акцент на самостоятельную деятельность учащихся, развитие их языковой личности и коммуникативных умений.

Современные школьники воспринимают информацию в визуальном и интерактивном формате. Применение интерактивных досок, обучающих платформ, онлайн-тестов и мультфильмов на уроках русского языка помогает разнообразить подачу материала.

Пример: при изучении пунктуации учащимся предлагается интерактивный видеоролик с задачей вставить знаки препинания в текст сказки. Такой подход способствует лучшему пониманию и запоминанию правил.

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BOSHLANG‘ICH TA‘LIM YO‘NALISHIDA XORIJIY TIL O‘QITISHDA INDIVIDUAL YONDASHUVNING SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada boshlang‘ich ta‘lim tizimida xorijiy tilni, xususan ingliz tilini o‘qitishda individual yondashuvning o‘rni, usullari va samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Har bir o‘quvchining individual psixologik va didaktik xususiyatlarini inobatga olgan holda xorijiy tilni o‘rgatish o‘quv jarayonining sifatini oshirishi, o‘quvchining bilimga bo‘lgan qiziqishi va ishtiyoqini kuchaytirishi mumkinligi asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: individual yondashuv, xorijiy til, boshlang‘ich ta‘lim, til o‘rganish, metodika, differensial yondashuv, o‘yinli texnologiyalar.

Zamonaviy ta‘lim jarayonida xorijiy tillarni, ayniqsa ingliz tilini erta yoshdan o‘rgatish masalasi dolzarb bo‘lib bormoqda. Shu bilan birga, bu jarayonda har bir o‘quvchining individual xususiyatlariga e‘tibor berish o‘qituvchidan yuqori pedagogik mahorat va metodik tayyorgarlikni talab qiladi. Individual yondashuv - bu o‘quvchilarning yoshi, bilim darajasi, psixologik holati, qiziqishlari, ehtiyojlari va o‘rganish sur‘atlarini inobatga olgan holda o‘qitishdir. Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilari bir xil darsda qatnashsalar ham, ularning tili o‘rganishga bo‘lgan qobiliyati, faolligi, lug‘at boyligi va xotira darajasi turlicha bo‘lishi mumkin. Shuning uchun bir xil metod bilan barcha o‘quvchilarga bir xil natija kutish noto‘g‘ri bo‘ladi.

Individual yondashuv xorijiy til o‘qitish sifatini oshiradi, chunki bu yondashuv orqali har bir o‘quvchining ehtiyojiga mos yondashiladi. Masalan, ba‘zi bolalar eshitish orqali yaxshi o‘rganadi, boshqalari esa ko‘rish yoki harakat (kinestetik) orqali. Shu sababli o‘qituvchi darsda turli xil metodik vositalardan: audiomateriallar, rasmlar, kartochkalar, harakatli o‘yinlar, dramatik sahnalar va interaktiv mashqlardan foydalanishi zarur. Bunday darslar bolalarda faollikni oshiradi, ishtirokni kuchaytiradi, eng muhimi – tilga bo‘lgan qiziqishni uyg‘otadi.

Bundan tashqari, individual yondashuvni ta‘minlashda differensial topshiriqlardan foydalanish juda muhim. Ya‘ni, o‘quvchilarga bilim darajasiga qarab turlicha murakkablikdagi topshiriqlar beriladi. Bu metod kuchli o‘quvchilarni zeriktirmaydi, sustroq o‘quvchilarga esa o‘z tempida ishlash imkonini beradi. Bu orqali o‘quvchilarning o‘ziga ishonchi ortadi, muvaffaqiyat hissi paydo bo‘ladi va bu ularni keyingi bilim olishga undaydi.

Shuningdek, boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilari uchun tilni o‘rgatishda o‘yinli metodlar alohida ahamiyatga ega. O‘yin bolalarning tabiiy faoliyati bo‘lib, ular o‘yin orqali ko‘proq bilim oladilar. Shuning uchun xorijiy til darslarini rolli o‘yinlar, interaktiv mashg‘ulotlar, jismoniy faoliyatni o‘z ichiga olgan mashqlar orqali olib borish tavsiya etiladi. Misol uchun, “Simon says” yoki “Touch the color” kabi inglizcha buyruq o‘yinlari nafaqat lug‘at boyligini oshiradi, balki eshitish va tushunish ko‘nikmalarini ham rivojlantiradi.

Individual yondashuvni samarali tashkil qilishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) ham muhim o‘rin tutadi. Multimedia vositalari, animatsiyalar, mobil ilovalar orqali bolalar mustaqil tarzda yoki kichik guruhda til o‘rganishda faol bo‘ladilar. Shuningdek, til o‘rganishga mo‘ljallangan veb-platformalar (masalan, Duolingo Kids,

Lingokids) orqali har bir o‘quvchi o‘z darajasiga mos materiallarni bajara oladi. Bu holat ham individual yondashuvga xizmat qiladi.

O‘qituvchining asosiy vazifasi - o‘quvchining individual imkoniyatlarini to‘g‘ri aniqlash, tahlil qilish va unga mos metodik strategiyalarni qo‘llashdan iborat. Bu jarayonda o‘qituvchi muntazam ravishda kuzatuv olib borishi, o‘quvchilar portfoliolarini yuritishi, ularga shaxsiy fikr bildirishi lozim. Aynan shunday faoliyat o‘quvchilar bilimini rivojlantiradi, mustaqil fikrlashga, tilni muloqot vositasi sifatida ishlatishga o‘rgatadi.

Boshlang‘ich ta’limda individual yondashuv nafaqat o‘qitish uslubini tanlashda, balki aholash, muloqot va motivatsiya tizimini shakllantirishda ham muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ko‘plab xorijiy pedagogik tajribalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, o‘quvchilarning til o‘rganishga bo‘lgan munosabati ko‘pincha ularga nisbatan qanday yondashilganiga bog‘liq bo‘ladi.

Masalan, Finlyandiya, Janubiy Koreya, Yaponiya va boshqa rivojlangan davlatlarda boshlang‘ich bosqichda individual yondashuv asosida til o‘rganish ko‘proq guruhlarda emas, balki shaxsga yo‘naltirilgan strategiyalar bilan olib boriladi. Ularda o‘quvchining o‘z-o‘zini baholash, refleksiya qilish (ya’ni o‘rganish jarayonini tahlil qilish) ko‘nikmalari ham dastlabki bosqichlardan boshlab shakllantiriladi. Bu esa bolaning o‘z kuchiga ishonch uyg‘otishiga va til o‘rganishga ijobiy ruhda yondashishiga sabab bo‘ladi.

O‘zbekistonda ham so‘nggi yillarda ta’lim sohasida olib borilayotgan islohotlar, ayniqsa, xorijiy tillarni erta yoshdan o‘qitish siyosati individual yondashuv tamoyillarini joriy qilishga katta imkoniyat yaratmoqda. Prezident qarorlari va vazirlik tavsiyalarida o‘quvchilarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olish, ko‘p tarmoqli metodlardan foydalanish, baholashda og‘zaki nutq, tinglab tushunish, o‘qish va yozish kabi ko‘nikmalarni alohida rivojlantirish zarurligi ta’kidlanmoqda.

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CURRENT ISSUES OF SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH IN MODERN LITERARY STUDIES

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Annotation: Modern literary studies are experiencing profound methodological, epistemological, and technological transformations. In the face of globalisation, digitalisation, and the rise of transdisciplinary approaches, the field is undergoing a rethinking of its

theoretical and scientific foundations. This paper explores some of the most urgent and complex issues currently confronting literary studies: the shift from “grand theory” to methodological pluralism, the growing role of digital humanities and computational tools, the intersection with cognitive and empirical sciences, and the challenges of transnational literary research. We argue that the future of literary scholarship lies in a dynamic synthesis of hermeneutics, data-driven methods, and global perspectives, where theory is not abandoned but reimagined.

Keywords: literary theory, digital humanities, interdisciplinary, cognitive poetics, post-theory, world literature, methodology

In recent decades, the landscape of literary studies has undergone rapid and multidirectional changes. Once dominated by strong theoretical schools-structuralism, Marxist criticism, psychoanalysis, post structuralism-contemporary literary research is now characterized by a plurality of approaches, fragmented theoretical discourses, and a methodological openness unprecedented in the field’s history.

At the same time, the emergence of digital technologies, global literary markets, and cognitive-scientific approaches has significantly reshaped both the object of literary studies and its methods of inquiry. These developments have opened new possibilities but also raised profound questions: How should we read in the digital age? What is the role of theory in an era of algorithmic analysis? Can we study global literatures without reproducing cultural hierarchies? Is interpretation still the core of our discipline?

This paper aims to explore these and related questions, identifying the most pressing scientific and theoretical challenges in modern literary studies and proposing directions for their critical resolution.

The latter half of the twentieth century saw literary studies governed by powerful theoretical paradigms. Whether it was the structuralism pursuit of deep linguistic systems, the Marxist emphasis on ideology and class, or the poststructuralist celebration of textual instability, each movement offered a totalising framework for reading and interpreting literature. However, by the early 2000s, these paradigms began to fracture. Literary critics such as Rita Felski, in works like *The Limits of Critique* (2015), called for a move beyond the “hermeneutics of suspicion” toward more generous, affective, and non-reductive reading practices. Scholars began speaking of a “post-theoretical” or “post-critical” era-not meaning the abandonment of theory, but a shift toward pragmatic, pluralistic, and locally grounded methodologies.

Today’s literary research often blends tools from multiple traditions-combining feminist theory with cognitive science, close reading with corpus linguistics, Eco criticism with postcolonial analysis. While this pluralism enriches the field, it also demands a renewed attention to methodological coherence and theoretical transparency.

Perhaps the most dramatic shift in recent literary research has come from the development of digital humanities (DH). Under this broad term, scholars explore ways to apply computational tools-such as natural language processing, stylometry, machine learning, and network analysis-to literary texts. Franco Moretti’s notion of “distant reading” (2013) set the stage for many of these innovations. Rather than close-read a single novel, Moretti proposed examining thousands of texts to uncover macroscopic patterns-in genre, narrative structure, intertextuality, and reception.

Recent works exemplify the power of these approaches: Barré (2024) analyzed over 12,000 French literary texts using embedding models, revealing the latent intertextual structures of 19th and 20th-century fiction.

One of the most significant issues is the globalisation of literary studies. The growing interest in world literature, translation studies, and transnational networks reflects a need to study literature beyond national canons and linguistic borders. Scholars like David Damrosch define world literature as a mode of circulation and reading rather than a canon. This perspective allows for a fluid, processual understanding of how texts move, are translated, and gain meaning in different cultural contexts.

The task before scholars is to build bridges between methodologies, between local and global literatures, between humanistic insight and scientific precision. In doing so, we affirm the enduring relevance of literary studies in making sense of texts-and of the world they reflect and transform.

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LINGUISTIC AND SOCIOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE CATEGORY OF ADDRESS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article explores the linguistic and sociolinguistic features of the category of address in both English and Uzbek languages. Addressing plays a crucial role in communication, reflecting social relationships, power dynamics, and cultural norms. By examining pronouns, honorifics, kinship terms, and politeness strategies, we aim to elucidate the intricate ways in which speakers navigate interpersonal interactions in these two languages.

Keywords: category, communication, reflecting social relationships, power dynamics, cultural norms.

Introduction. Addressing individuals in English involves a variety of linguistic features that reflect the speaker's relationship with the addressee and the context of communication. From pronouns to honorifics, these features play a crucial role in conveying social dynamics and establishing rapport. This section explores some of the key linguistic features of address in English.

1. Pronouns. One of the fundamental linguistic features of address in English is the use of pronouns. The most common pronoun used for addressing individuals is "you." Unlike some languages that have formal and informal pronouns, English generally lacks such grammatical distinctions. However, variations in pronoun usage can still convey nuances of formality and familiarity. For example, "you" is used in both formal and informal contexts, but the tone and register of speech may vary depending on the relationship between the

speakers. Additionally, regional dialects or cultural influences may introduce variations in pronoun usage, such as "y'all" in Southern American English for addressing a group of people [1].

2. Titles and Honorifics. In formal contexts, English speakers often use titles and honorifics to address individuals with respect. These titles typically precede the individual's last name and convey their professional or social status. For instance, "Mr." is used to address men, "Mrs." or "Ms." for married or unmarried women respectively, and "Dr." for individuals with a doctoral degree. Titles like "Sir" or "Madam" may also be used in polite or formal communication when the speaker does not know the addressee's name. In professional settings, such as business or academia, the appropriate use of titles is considered essential for maintaining decorum and showing respect.

3. Use of Names. In informal contexts, English speakers may opt to use first names or even nicknames when addressing each other. Using someone's first name is a sign of familiarity and closeness, commonly seen among friends, family members, or colleagues. Nicknames, on the other hand, are often based on personal characteristics or shared experiences and can further strengthen bonds between individuals. However, it's important to note that the use of names varies depending on cultural norms and personal preferences, and individuals may have different preferences regarding how they prefer to be addressed.

4. Tone and Register. The tone and register of speech also play a significant role in addressing individuals in English. Formal situations typically require a more polite and respectful tone, characterized by the use of complete sentences, formal language, and appropriate titles or honorifics. In contrast, informal situations allow for a more relaxed and casual tone, with speakers using colloquial expressions, slang, or even humor. The choice of tone and register depends on factors such as the setting, the relationship between speakers, and the level of formality required.

In conclusion, the linguistic features of address in English encompass a range of elements, including pronouns, titles, names, and tone. These features serve as linguistic markers that convey social relationships, power dynamics, and cultural norms in communication. Understanding how to navigate these linguistic features effectively is essential for successful interpersonal interactions in English-speaking contexts.

As a starting point, this essay is expected to provide a profound background of English and Uzbek languages, which might be crucial for a better understanding of the linguistic and sociolinguistic aspects described in the following sections. It will illustrate not only how languages have evolved over the centuries, but also the variety of contexts in which they are spoken as well as highlight the status of each language in the contemporary world. English is a member of the Germanic language family, which in turn comprises a part of the Indo-European language family. It is closely related to Frisian, Dutch, and German, and in terms of writing systems, the English language is based on the Roman alphabet, whilst including several digraphs, such as 'ch', 'sh', 'ph' and 'th' and ligatures, such as 'oe', 'ae' and 'd'. Modern English, through the spread of the British Empire, has become the world's dominant global language, with some 400 million native speakers and a further 800 million people who use English as a second language. On the other hand, Uzbek belongs to the Turkic language family, more specifically, the Karluk branch. It has been influenced by Persian, Tajik, and Russian and there are many dialects-often a source of heated nationalistic debates. The Arabic/Persian-based script was used until the arrival of the Russians in the 19th century when a modified version of the Cyrillic alphabet was introduced.

Studying discourse can reveal a great deal about a society's values, beliefs, and social structure. Discourse shapes our ways of thought and always reflects society and various social

issues. Studying discourse may help people to better understand other people, as it's a way of understanding the world. By learning the language of a specific discourse, one can come to master this type of social performance presented in the discourse. For example, if one wants to assess the credibility of a political leader, he or she will enter the discourse of politics and listen to the language employed by that political leader. As a widely used academic tool, studying discourse is also the research interest of many professionals in different fields. For example, social workers can benefit from the studies of discourse because it can guide social workers to uncover facts, diagnose behavior, and select interventions for the client in each step of solving problems. It gives the profession a scope for explaining and influencing social policy. Also, by directing attention to the most significant facets of a topic, discourse frames and limits the ways social workers think and act on that topic. The same thing happens in the practices of discourse analysis throughout the entire field. Social workers attempt to understand how the social construction of knowledge influences how power is used and allocated in society. Through the practices of discourse analysis, social workers begin to reconstruct knowledge so that it can be used to promote social justice, quality of life, and the well-being of humanity.

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«СОЛНЦЕ» КАК ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЙ ОБРАЗ

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Аннотация: в статье исследуются синтез смысла определяемого слова «СОЛНЦЕ» со зрительным образом, задействованные в названиях произведений Алишера Навои. В статье используется метод аналитического исследования. Выводы автора вполне обоснованы.

Ключевые слова: астрономические термины: Солнце, Луна, Звезды, Месяц; лунолика; брови, как месяц;;улыбка, как солнце; глаза, как звезды.

Одна из характерных черт языка Навои состоит в чрезвычайной распространенности в нем определенных сочетаний, в которых сближаются понятия, не имеющие реальной связи или зависимости, но пересечение которых создает синтез смысла определяемого слова со зрительным образом, который несет определяемого слово. Окружающий поэта мир рождает у него целую цепь поэтических представлений, переданных с помощью астрономических терминов: небо кажется ему опрокинутой чашей, смятение чувств сравнивается с сумятицей базара. Светлый мир наполнен отражениями: блески солнца сверкают в каплях воды или вина, свет луны отражен в облике возлюбленной...

В поэзии Навои широко используются астрономические термины: Солнце, Луна, Звезды, Месяц. Сама возлюбленная не иначе как луноликая, брови, как месяц, улыбка, как солнце, глаза, как звезды.

Украшенье золотое над изгибами бровей
Иль звезда и полумесяц - светлый лик красы твоей?
Это складки покрывала, что по ветру развиты,
Или крылья нежной пери, чтоб лететь ветров быстрее?

Мы подробнее остановимся на использовании в газелях поэта самого величественного явления природы - солнца для мотивировки худо- жественного образа, проанализируем отношение поэта к использованию небесных светил в контексте его лирических произведений.

Образ идеального правителя осмысливается Навои как самое величественное явление природы - солнце, именно оно борется с самыми страшными пороками.

Лирика Навои демонстрирует его особое отношение к женщине. Красота, чистота и благочестие женщины украшают мир, как солнце. В словесной структуре языка Навои непременно присутствует точная мотивировка каждого образа, что подчеркивает одну из сильнейших сторон его поэтического таланта. Способы создания внутренней мотивировки того или иного образа в произведениях Навои разнообразны и оригинальны.

В арабском языке Солнце - женского рода, поэтому сравнение женщины с солнцем обосновано не только характерологической оценкой, но и общностью грамматической категории рода.

Каждая поэтическая строка Навои - это целостное поэтическое единство, которое достигается виртуозным владением всеми потенциальными возможностями языка, умением наполнить живым смыслом те его элементы, которые самостоятельного значения не имеют. Это позволяет Навои создавать удивительные по своей насыщенности, поэтической логике строки:

**Бог волею своей дал тебе лик, что солнце.
Дал месяцы бровей - дар, все сердца гнетущий.**

Мастер изумительных афористических человеческих образов Навои не менее силен и в создании широко и последовательно развернутых образов природы. Вот как он дает картину необычно знойного лета:

Конец джауза. Ветер раскален,
Все обжигает он со всех сторон;
И небо, словно печь, раскалено,
И солнце, как язык огня, красно.
Заря вздувает пламя, словно мех,
Ночь подсыпает уголь без помех;
Не метеоры падают в ночи,
То искры вылетают из печи...

В рассказе о походе против хана Маллу большое место уделено Средней Азии и Хорасану, родине Навои. С теплотой и мастерски изображает поэт места, где проходила его жизнь.

Как солнце посреди планет своих,
Так Хорасан срьель поясов земных.
А в Хорасане - величавый град,
Прекрасная душа - его Герат...

«Язык птиц» (Лисон - уттайр) - сложная философская поэма, в которой посредством аллегорических образов и богатой символики Навои излагает свои взгляды на действительность, религию и многие другие важнейшие вопросы жизни. В центре его поэмы находится человек - тень бога. Но тень полная мудрости и сознания. Во всех его описаниях важнейшую роль играют астрокосмические термины и производные от них эпитеты:

Как сокровище, скрыт он , и суть его - тайна,
Блещет в зеркале мира красы его тайна.
И когда он явить себя миру решил,
Он затмил своим блеском сиянье светил.
И в лучах его солнцеподобного блеска
Сто миллионов теней обозначились резко.
И к теням, засверкавшим по дальним просторам,
Вездесушим своим обратился он взором.

Итак, слово «солнце» у Навои использовано в нескольких значениях: в значении образа идеального правителя, женщины, в прямом смысле - как природное светило, в значении родины Навои Хорасана, лика и красоты возлюбленной, в значении человека. Такие метафоры и его эпитеты придают поэтической речи Навои высокую стилистическую окраску, позволяют поэту выделить в явлении какую-то одну его сторону и придать ей осязаемый зримый облик, что способствует достижению поэтической достоверности стиха, выразительности и убедительности авторской мысли.

Непостижимые по глубине, мудрости и красоте произведения Алишера Навои звучат современно, благозвучно и являются непревзойденными образцами восточной поэзии, на которые равняется не одно поколение поэтов!

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЗРИТЕЛЬНОЙ НАГЛЯДНОСТИ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА УРОКАХ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В СРЕДНИХ КЛАССАХ (ЗРИТЕЛЬНАЯ НАГЛЯДНОСТЬ И ТСО НА УРОКАХ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В СРЕДНИХ КЛАССАХ)

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Аннотаци: Статья посвящена актуальной проблеме использования зрительной наглядности и технических средств обучения (ТСО) на уроках литературы в средних классах общеобразовательной школы. Рассматривается роль дидактического принципа наглядности в процессе литературного образования, а также анализируются возможности традиционных и современных (мультимедийных) средств визуализации учебного материала. Обосновывается, что комплексное и целенаправленное применение зрительной наглядности и ТСО способствует более глубокому восприятию художественного текста, формированию целостных образов, развитию критического мышления и повышению мотивации учащихся к изучению предмета.

Ключевые слова: зрительная наглядность, технические средства обучения (ТСО), методика преподавания литературы, средние классы, дидактический принцип наглядности, мультимедийные технологии, активизация познавательной деятельности.

ВВЕДЕНИЕ

Проблема активизации учебно-познавательной деятельности школьников на уроках литературы является одной из центральных в современной педагогике. Изучение литературы в средних классах (5-9 классы) сопряжено с необходимостью формирования образного мышления, эмоционального отклика на прочитанное и понимания сложных социокультурных контекстов [3, с.15]. Художественное произведение, будучи уникальным явлением искусства слова, требует от учащегося развитого воображения и способности к мысленному воссозданию описываемых событий, персонажей и среды.

В этом контексте принцип наглядности, являющийся одним из основополагающих в дидактике, приобретает особое значение. Наглядность в преподавании литературы выходит за рамки простой иллюстрации и выступает в качестве мощного средства, компенсирующего отсутствие прямого чувственного опыта, необходимого для адекватного восприятия литературных образов [6, с.42]. Использование как традиционной зрительной наглядности, так и современных технических средств обучения (ТСО) позволяет создать полисенсорную среду обучения, что особенно важно для подростков с их наглядно-образным типом мышления.

Цель данной статьи – проанализировать особенности и эффективность применения зрительной наглядности и ТСО на уроках литературы в средних классах и определить их потенциал для оптимизации образовательного процесса.

Теоретические основы использования наглядности в преподавании литературы. Принцип наглядности (от лат. *visualis* – зрительный) основывается на идее о том, что эффективное обучение предполагает привлечение органов чувств, в первую очередь зрительного и слухового восприятия, к процессу усвоения знаний. Я.А. Коменский, И.Г. Песталоцци, К.Д. Ушинский [9, с.40] подчеркивали, что конкретные образы, воспринимаемые с помощью органов чувств, являются основой для формирования абстрактных понятий.

В методике преподавания литературы наглядность выполняет следующие ключевые функции:

Иллюстративная- помогает конкретизировать и образно представить неясные или абстрактные элементы художественного произведения (исторические реалии, бытовые детали, внешний вид персонажей, пейзажи).

Информативная (источниковедческая)- служит самостоятельным источником знаний, например, при изучении биографии писателя (портреты, рукописи, мемориальные места) или при сопоставлении разных видов искусства (репродукции картин, музыкальные фрагменты).

Мотивационная и активизирующая - способствует привлечению внимания, стимулирует эмоциональный отклик и познавательный интерес, создает проблемные ситуации [1, с.507].

Развивающая - способствует развитию воображения, наблюдательности, эстетического вкуса и навыков анализа [3, с.25].

Традиционная зрительная наглядность включает:

- ❖ печатные иллюстрации (репродукции картин, рисунки, схемы);
- ❖ портреты писателей;
- ❖ географические карты;
- ❖ раздаточный материал.

Эти средства незаменимы, поскольку позволяют учащимся детально рассмотреть и проанализировать статический образ.

Применение технических средств обучения (ТСО) на уроках литературы.

Технические средства обучения, особенно аудиовизуальные и мультимедийные, значительно расширяют возможности реализации принципа наглядности [8, с.574]. В средних классах наиболее востребованными являются:

Экранные средства (диафильмы, слайды, презентации): позволяют систематизировать учебный материал, обеспечить логичность изложения и создать динамическую визуализацию [5, с.88]. Мультимедийные презентации (PowerPoint, Google Slides) эффективно используются для биографических справок, анализа композиции, характеристики персонажей и литературоведческих понятий.

Видео- и аудиосредства (учебные фильмы, экранизации, аудиокниги, документальные кадры) - незаменимы для погружения в атмосферу эпохи, визуализации сложных сцен, знакомства с авторским чтением или театральными интерпретациями. Демонстрация фрагментов экранизаций может стать основой для сравнительного анализа и критической оценки режиссерского видения и авторского замысла.

Цифровые образовательные ресурсы (ЦОР) и интернет – ресурсы- интерактивные карты, виртуальные экскурсии по музеям и мемориальным усадьбам, электронные энциклопедии и интерактивные задания. Эти ресурсы способствуют самостоятельной работе учащихся и индивидуализации обучения [5, с.120].

Использование ТСО требует от учителя не простого показа материала, а его методически обоснованного включения в структуру урока. Мультимедийные средства должны выступать не как развлекательный элемент, а как инструмент для решения конкретных дидактических задач. Например, для анализа лирического произведения эффективно сочетание текста, музыкального сопровождения и зрительного ряда (репродукции живописи), что позволяет создать комплексное восприятие.

Эффективность использования зрительной наглядности и ТСО в средних классах.

Опыт показывает, что комплексное применение зрительной наглядности и ТСО на уроках литературы в средних классах ведет к следующим положительным результатам:

Повышение качества восприятия - зрительный образ, соотнесенный с художественным словом, делает восприятие более полным и глубоким, облегчает понимание метафор и скрытых смыслов [2, с.20].

Развитие коммуникативных навыков - обсуждение увиденного (иллюстрации, фрагмента фильма) стимулирует устную речь, навыки аргументации и выражения личной позиции.

Оптимизация учебного времени - визуализация большого объема информации (например, исторического фона) происходит быстрее и эффективнее, чем исключительно словесное описание.

Интеграция предметов - использование наглядности способствует межпредметным связям (литература-история-МХК-география), формируя целостное представление о культуре и мире.

Ключевым методическим условием эффективности является дозированность и целесообразность использования наглядности. Избыток визуального материала может отвлечь от основного объекта изучения – художественного текста. Зрительная наглядность и ТСО должны служить средством анализа текста, а не его заменой.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ

Таким образом, использование зрительной наглядности и технических средств обучения на уроках литературы в средних классах является не просто данью моде, а необходимостью, продиктованной современными требованиями к образовательному процессу и психологическими особенностями учащихся. Интеграция традиционных и мультимедийных средств визуализации позволяет качественно улучшить процесс изучения литературы: сделать его более наглядным, эмоциональным, познавательно насыщенным и мотивирующим [1, с.510]. Дальнейшие исследования в этой области должны быть направлены на разработку новых, интерактивных форм использования ЦОР и ТСО, максимально интегрированных в самостоятельную и проектную деятельность школьников.

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SIFATNI IFODALOVCHI FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING O‘ZBEK XALQ OG‘ZAKI IJODIDAGI O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xalq og‘zaki ijodida uchraydigan sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologizmlar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Frazeologiyalarni tarjima qilishda milliy va madaniy omillarga e‘tibor beriladi. Shuningdek, bu boradagi ayrim muammolar yoritilib, misollar yordamida tushuntiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar. Milliy-madaniy, misollar, frazeologizmlar, og‘zaki ijod, muammolar, sifat, tarjima, tushuncha.

O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodi bir necha yillar davomida og‘izdan-og‘izga o‘tib kelayotgan[2,14-b] bo‘lsa-da, unda juda ko‘plab sifatni ifodalovchi frazemalarni uchratish mumkin. Bu xalq og‘zaki ijodi xalqning turmush tarzini, dunyoqarashini, orzu va umidlarini, dard va quvonchlarini yaqqol tasvirlaydi. Xalq og‘zaki ijodiga biz dostonlar, maqollar, topishmoqlar, afsonalar, rivoyatlar, latifalar ertaklar va xalq qo‘shiqlarini kiritishimiz mumkin[2,9-b]. Shuningdek, bu xalq og‘zaki ijodining ba‘zi namunalarida foydalanilgan frazemalar va tarixiy so‘zlar yo‘qolib borishining oldini olish va kelgusi avlodlarga yetkazishda o‘rni katta.

Frazeologizmlar - tilshunoslikning bir muhim bo‘limi hisoblanadi[7,54-b]. Unda insonlarning his-tuyg‘ularini, kayfiyatini, shaxsiy va ijtimoiy holatlarini ifodalashi mumkin. Sifatni ifodalab keluvchi frazeologizmlardan xalq og‘zaki ijodida ham keng qo‘llanilib kelinmoqda.

Tilshunoslikda, frazeologizmlarga xalq og‘zaki ijod namunasi sifatida ham qarashimiz mumkin. Chunki, ular ham asrlar davomida insonlarning turmush tarzini va dunyoqarashini ifodalashda o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lgan va insonlar o‘rtasida shakllanib borgan. Sifatni bildiruvchi frazeologizmlar, asosan, obrazlilik, kuchaytirish, baholash, emotsional va boshqa holatlarini uchratishimiz mumkin[7,78-b]. Shuningdek, ular tasvirli yo‘l bilan ifodalanadi. O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodidan ayrimlarini ko‘rib chiqadigan bo‘lsak[2,145-b]:

Frazeologiyalar	Ma‘nosi	Belgilayotgan sifat
Qo‘li ochiq	saxiy	saxovatlilik
Ko‘ngli to‘q	sabrli, minnatdor	barqarorlik
Ko‘ngli dengizdek	saxovatli	mehribonlik
Og‘zi qulog‘ida	juda xursand	quvonchli holat
Boshi osmonda	g‘ururlangan	mag‘rurlik
Yuragi keng	bag‘rikeng	insonparvarlik

Ular insoniy sifatlarni ifodalash bilan birga unga hissiy rang ham bermoqda. Frazeologizmlar sifatlarni ifodalashda bir qancha bosqichlarni bajaradi. Kuchaytirish (“oq yuzli”, “tosh yurak”, “og‘zi qulog‘ida”) belgining ma‘nosini kuchaytirishga xizmat qilyapti[4,61-b]. Baholash (“ko‘ngli to‘q” –ijobiy, “ko‘zi qizil”-salbiy) orqali qahramonga axloqiy baho berilmoqda[4,63-b]. Obrazlilik esa qahramonning ichki dunyosini tasvirlaydi. Masalan, “yuragi po‘latdek” – jasurlikni kuchli obrazda yoritmoqda[4,70-b]. Emotsionallik-kitobxonni his tuyg‘ulari orqali qahramonning nutqini jonlantira olishlikdir[4.75-b]. “Alpomish”, “Kuntug‘mish”, “Go‘rog‘li” va “Ravshan” kabi dostonlarda keng qo‘llaniladi.

Sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologiyalarni maqollar tasnifida ko‘rib chiqsak: “qo‘li ochiq – elga yoqadi” va “tosh yurakning ko‘zi yosh ko‘rmas”[3,54-b] kabi misollarni oladigan bo‘lsak, bu iboralar orqali kim yomon yoki kim yaxshi ekanligini axloqiy sifatlar bilan baholayapti. Maqollarda, asosan, frazeologizmlar metafora va sifatni baholovchi vazifasida keladi. Shuningdek, frazeologizmlar bilan bir nechta olimlar shug‘ullangan. Bu soha bilan V.V.Vinogradov, A.V. Kunin, A.M. Babayev, Sh. Rahmatullayev va M. Asqarova kabi tilshunos olimlardir. Vinogradov frazeologiyaning nazariy poydevorini qo‘yib bergan bo‘lsa, Kunin uni mustaqil fan sifatida asoslagan[6,5-8-b]. Sh. Rahmatullayev esa o‘zbek frazeologiyasining asoschisi bo‘lib, uni nutq bilan bog‘lagan va milliy til tizimida mukammal o‘rgangan.

Hozirgi kunda sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologizmlarda bir qancha muammolar mavjud. Birinchidan, frazeologizmlarni umumiy tilda o‘rganish mumkin, ammo sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologiyalarni o‘rganishda alohida ahamiyat berilmagan. Ikkinchi sabab esa, frazeologik lug‘atlar mavjud bo‘lsa ham, ularning ba‘zilari janrli tahlil (doston, ertak, maqol) asosida tuzilmagan[4,82-b] va natijada xalq og‘zaki ijodidagi iboralar yo‘qolishiga sabab bo‘lgan. Uchinchidan esa, ko‘plab darslik va manbalarda frazeologiyalar tahlil darajasida emas, balki misol sifatida berilgan[7,56-b]. Shu boisdan, o‘zbek tili frazeologizmlarida sifatni ifodalovchi birliklar bo‘yicha maxsus tematik lug‘at tuzish va ularni badiiy asarlarda tahlil qilish dolzarb masala sanaladi.

Frazeologizmlar – tildagi barqaror so‘z birikmasi bo‘lib, ularning ma‘nosi jihatdan butunlikni hosil qiladi va tarkibidagi so‘zlar ma‘no mustaqilligini yo‘qotadi[4,72-b]. Frazeologiyalar orqali xalqning hayotini, milliy – madaniy qadriyatlarini va tafakkurini yaqqol ochib beradi[4,85-b] va insonlarning fe‘l –atvorini, tashqi ko‘rinishlarini ifodalashda, tildagi badiiy estetik imkoniyatlarini boyitishda katta ahamiyatga ega.

O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodi namunalari ko‘p bo‘lsa-da, ulardan biri bo‘lgan “Alpomish” dostoni sifatida sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologizmlarga e‘tibor qaratsak. Masalan:

- Ko‘p odamlarni ham xafa qilar, nima bo‘lsa musofir-da, boylarning ko‘nglini ozor qilar[1,46-b].

Bu yerda “ko‘ngli norozi bo‘lish” – xafa bo‘lish, ranjish ma‘nolarini ifodalamoqda.

- Oh urganda xasta ko‘nglin xushladi[1,107-b].

“Ko‘ngli xushlandi” frazeologizm bo‘lib, xursand bo‘ldi, mamnun bo‘ldi ma‘nolarini ifodalamoqda.

- Shul zamon egniga qoqib tashladi[1,107-b].

Uzoq yillik g‘am – tashvishlaridan xalos bo‘ldi ya‘ni yengil tortdi, taskin topdi degan ma‘nolarini ifodalamoqda.

- Alpomish bandi ketganiga necha vaqt o‘tgan, hammaning ham ko‘nglidan chiqib ketgan[1,330-b].

Ko‘nglidan chiqib ketmoq frazeologizm bo‘lib, bu yoqtirmay qo‘ygan his- tuyg‘usini ifodalab kelmoqda.

“Alpomish” dostonidagi qahramonlarni fazilatlarini va xarakterini sifatni ifodalovchi frazeologizmlar orqali yoritadigan bo‘lsak, ular quyidagicha:

Alpomish – yuragi tog‘dek, ko‘zi yiltillab qaragan, dadil.

Barchinoy – ko‘ngli daryo, yuzini yorug‘ tutgan.

Qalmoqshoh – yuzini burib, qat‘iy.

Qultoy – ko‘ngli hushlangan.

Frazeologizmlar nafaqat balki sifatni balki turli grammatik ma‘no turlarini ifodalashi mumkin. Ular sifat, harakat (fe‘l) holat, miqdor, his-tuyg‘u, vaqt va munosabat kabi ma‘nolarni bildiradi.

Harakatni (fe'l) ifodalovchi frazeologizmlar amal, harakat, holatni bildiradi. (ko'z yumdi, bosh ko'tardi). Holni ifodalovchilar amal qanday bajarilganini bildiradi (yashin tezligida, ko'z ochib yumguncha). Miqdor – darajani ifodalagan frazeologiyalar esa ko'pligi, kamligi, yoki ortiqligini bildiradi. (bir og'iz gap, ko'pdan beri). Vaqtni bildirib kelgan frazeologiyalar bo'lsa, amal yoki hodisaning vaqtini bildiradi (bir mahal, tong otmasdan). His-tuyg'uni ifodalagan frazeologiyalar, asosan, ruhiy kechirma yoki hissiyotni ifodalaydi (ko'ngli to'ldi, yuragi ezildi). Ichki hissiy munosabatlarini ifodalaydigan frazeologiyalar (bosh egdi, ko'nglidan o'tdi) munosabatni ifodalashini ko'rishimiz mumkin[7,92-93-b].

Umumiy qilib olganda, tilshunoslikning muhim bo'limlaridan biri bu- frazeologiyadir. Asosiy vazifalariga tildagi frazeologizmlarni yig'ish va o'rganish, ularning ma'no, tuzilish, uslubiy xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish, leksik birlik sifatida izohlash, badiiy, so'zlashuv va yozma nutqdagi o'rnini ifodalashdan iborat. Shuningdek, tilda ifoda go'zalligini oshirishi, milliylikni, dunyoqarashni, urf-odatlarini aks ettirishi, nutqni boyitishi va jonlantirishi mumkin. Sifat frazeologizmlar predmetning belgisi, xususiyati, tashqi ko'rinishi yoki ichki holatini ifodalovchi barqaror iboralardir. Bular oddiy so'zlar o'rnida kelib, ko'chma ma'no ifodalaydi[5,343-b]. Bularni xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalarida ko'plab uchratishimiz mumkin.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ПАРЕНТЕТИЧЕСКИХ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ В РУССКОМ, УЗБЕКСКОМ И АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ.

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается сравнительный анализ функциональных особенностей парентетических внесений в русском, узбекском и азербайджанском языках. Рассмотрен вопрос структуры парентетических конструкций. Раскрываются основные значения парентезы.

Ключевые слова: парентеза, парентетические конструкции, функция, особенности, русский язык, узбекский язык, азербайджанский язык, прагматическая функция.

Синтаксис обладает богатейшими стилистическими возможностями. По мнению М. А. К. Халлидея, «синтаксические конструкции, актуализированные благодаря определенному выбору, могут служить средством, с помощью которого писатель передает свое видение мира, и, возможно, даже наиболее эффективным средством» [3,

с. 138]. Стилистическая функция обуславливает отбор языковых средств в целях достижения желаемого воздействия на читателя [1, с. 13].

Парентетические конструкции относятся к синтаксическим средствам языка, употребление которых играет важную роль в передаче авторской позиции. Они придают тексту эмоциональность, убедительность, позволяют выделить важную информацию, сократить избыточные лексические единицы, задать определенный темп прочтения.

Перентетические конструкции представляют собой включение в основное предложение конструкции (слова, словосочетания или предложения), связанного с ним не грамматически, а содержательно-ассоциативно [2, с. 79]. При произношении данные конструкции выделены интонационно, характеризуясь понижением тона и, как правило, убыстрением темпа речи, их границы подчеркиваются паузами, а на письме – пунктуационно, обычно посредством тире или скобок.

По своей структуре парентезы очень разнообразны: они могут быть представлены как отдельными словами или словосочетаниями, так и простыми и даже сложными предложениями.

В коммуникативном аспекте парентетические конструкции способны выражать различную коммуникативно-целевую семантику: повествование, вопрос, побуждение.

Прагматическая функция парентетических конструкций заключается в коммуникативном введении содержания, в сообщении уточнительных и дополнительных сведений, которые выражают различную коммуникативно-целевую семантику.

Парентезы используются как самостоятельно, так и в сочетании с другими средствами экспрессивного синтаксиса.

Парентетические конструкции выполняют ряд функциональных задач: уточняют или дополняют основную мысль, выражают дополнительные сведения, замечания, поправки или пояснения, а также влияют на эмоциональную окраску текста, выражая эмоции и подчеркивая важность сказанного. Они служат для создания дополнительного смыслового слоя в предложении и используются в различных стилях речи, особенно в разговорном и публицистическом.

Основные функции парентетических конструкций добавление информации (они позволяют вставлять в текст дополнительные сведения или замечания, не нарушая при этом грамматическую структуру основного предложения), уточнение и пояснение (парентезы помогают сделать высказывание более точным, предоставляя пояснения или уточняющие детали к основной мысли), эмоциональная окраска (конструкции могут передавать отношение автора к высказыванию, усиливая эмоциональную нагрузку или подчеркивая важность определенного момента), авторская идентификация (в некоторых случаях парентезы могут служить для указания авторства или источника информации, выделяя её из основного текста), внесение поправок (они могут использоваться для внесения поправок или исправлений в уже сказанное, корректируя основную мысль в процессе изложения).

Сравнительный анализ функциональных особенностей парентетических конструкций в разных языках позволяет выявить универсальные закономерности и специфические черты, обусловленные типологическими различиями и культурными особенностями.

В русском, узбекском и азербайджанском языках парентетические конструкции характеризуются структурной обособленностью и интонационной выделенностью.

Несмотря на общие черты, существуют различия в частотности и способах выражения различных типов парентетических конструкций в рассматриваемых языках. Например, в русском языке более распространены вводные слова и словосочетания, выражающие модальность и оценку (*к счастью, к сожалению, без всякого сомнения*), в то время как в узбекском и азербайджанском языках чаще используются парентетические конструкции, указывающие на источник информации или выражающие уважение к собеседнику (*aytishlaricha, darhaqiqat, masalan; olsun ki, deməli, bir sözlə*).

В целом, в каждом из рассматриваемых языков можно выделить следующие основные типы парентетических конструкций (см. в таблице №1. Типы парентетических конструкций):

Таблица №1. Типы парентетических конструкций

уточняющие (по крайней мере, без преувеличения; <i>masalan, jumladan; guya, eşitdiyimə görə</i>)	конкретизируют или разъясняют предшествующую информацию
оценочные (разумеется, действительно; <i>balki, ehtimol; heyif ki, çox heyif ki</i>)	выражают отношение автора к сообщаемому
вводные (бывало, по обычию; <i>afsuski, hayriyat; sanki, elə bil</i>)	выражают модальность, степень уверенности, сомнение
соединительные (иными словами, коротко говоря; <i>xullas, demək; əvvələn, birincisi</i>)	устанавливают логическую связь между частями текста
цитирующие (говорят, передают; <i>menimcha, aytishlaricha; məncə, bizcə</i>)	указывают на источник информации.

Однако, способы выражения каждого из этих типов парентетических конструкций могут существенно различаться в рассматриваемых языках.

Сравнительный анализ прагматических функций парентетических конструкций в русском, узбекском и азербайджанском языках позволяет выявить как универсальные, так и специфические черты.

Универсальными функциями парентетических конструкций даны в таблице №2.

Таблица №2. Универсальные функции парентетических конструкций

смягчение высказывания	используются для снижения категоричности утверждения и выражения неуверенности
управление вниманием	используются для привлечения внимания к определенной части высказывания
выражение вежливости и уважения	в узбекском и азербайджанском языках соблюдение социальных норм играет важную роль, парентезы часто используются для выражения вежливости и уважения к собеседнику.

	В русском языке эта функция менее выражена.
подчеркивание личной ответственности	в русском языке скобки часто используются для подчеркивания личной ответственности за высказывание, в то время как в узбекском и азербайджанском языках предпочтение отдается более косвенным способам выражения.

Общими функциями парентетических конструкций являются (см. таблицу №3):

Таблица №2. Общие функции парентетических конструкций

структурирование дискурса	используются для разделения текста на отдельные смысловые блоки и обозначения переходов от одной мысли к другой
разъяснение контекста	предоставляют дополнительную информацию о контексте высказывания.

Специфические функции скобок, связанные с типологическими различиями языков, включают (см. таблицу №4):

Таблица №4. Специфические функции парентетических конструкций

выражение причинно-следственных связей	в русском языке для выражения причинно-следственных связей часто используются сложные предложения с подчинительными союзами, в то время как в узбекском и азербайджанском языках предпочтение отдается использованию скобок, указывающих на причину или следствие
выражение авторской позиции	в русском языке авторская позиция часто выражается с помощью вводных слов и словосочетаний, в то время как в узбекском и азербайджанском языках используются более косвенные способы выражения

Сравнительный анализ функциональных особенностей парентетических конструкций в русском, узбекском и азербайджанском языках позволяет выявить как универсальные, так и специфические черты. Универсальные функции парентетических конструкций связаны с необходимостью смягчения коммуникативной цели и управления вниманием адресата. Специфические функции парентетических конструкций обусловлены культурными особенностями и типологическими различиями языков.

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ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA O'ZBEK ADABIYOTINI O'QITISHGA YANGICHA YONDASHUV

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Annotatsiya

Bugungi zamon yoshlariga adabiy ta'lim berish, ularning tafakkurini rivojlantirish maqsadida qator adabiyotshunos olimlar tomonidan turli talqin va tahlillar berib borilmoqda. Badiiy adabiyotni qiyofasi o'zgargan zamon va sog'lom tafakkur nuqtayi nazaridan o'qish, idrok etish, tushunish va tahlil etish masalasi o'z yechimini kutayotgan dolzarb muammolardan biridir. Shunday ekan, adabiyotshunos olimlarimiz va munaqqidlarimizning o'z qarashlarini belgilab, tahlil va talqin tamoyillarini aniqlab olishga kirisha boshlashlari kerak, bu paydo bo'lgan yangicha fikrlash ilmiy tadqiqotning mutlaqo yangi nazariy asoslarini shakllantirish zarurati bor.

Maqolada Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshevning o'ziga xos uslubi haqida mulohazalar bayon qilingan. Olim badiiy asar haqidagi fikrlari va tahlillari bayonida faqatgina matnga tayanadi va ilmiy xulosalarini matndan keltirib xolis ifodalaydi. Asarning badiiyatiga qarab o'z xulosalarini bayon qilishi bilan birga asarda yo'l qo'yilgan kamchiliklarni ham bayon etishi xususida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: adabiyotshunoslik, badiiy tahlil, badiiy adabiyot, ma'naviy energiya, adabiy ta'lim, ilmiy haqiqat, estetik joziba, pedagogika, metodika, matn.

Inson ma'naviyatini shakllantirish imkoniyatining kattaligi va odamga ta'sir qudrati miqyosiga ko'ra badiiy adabiyot san'atning boshqa turlari orasida alohida mavqega ega. G'oyat ko'p o'lchovli murakkab butunlik bo'lmish badiiy adabiyot o'quvchi tomonidan o'qilib, his etilib, anglanib olingandagina ta'sirchan estetik-ma'naviy energiyaga aylanadi. His etilmagan, anglanmagan go'zallik hayotdagi foydalanilmagan imkoniyat kabi shaxs ma'naviyatiga ta'sir ko'rsata olmaydi. Shuning uchun ham oliy adabiy ta'limda badiiy asar tahlili alohida mavqega, ahamiyatga egadir. Adabiy ta'lim oldidagi bosh maqsadga erishish uchun filolog mutaxassis badiiy asarni tahlil qilish yo'llarini puxta egallab olishi shartdir. Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshev faoliyatini, chop etilgan maqolalarini kuzatgan kishi bunga to'la amin bo'ladi. Olimning har bir chiqishi badiiy asarni to'laroq tushunishga qaratilganligiga guvoh bo'ladi: "Yetuk badiiy matnlarning to'la anglanishi va badiiy tahlil qilinishiga erishmay turib, jamiyat miqyosida barkamol shaxs shakllantirishni o'ylash amalga oshmaydigan orzudir. Chinakam badiiy tahlil bo'lmagan joyda badiiy matn o'quvchining tuyg'ulariga ta'sir etmaydi, binobarin, shaxs ma'naviyati shakllanishiga xizmat qilmaydi".[1, 17-b]

Olim jamiyat a'zolarining biror ilmiy haqiqatni bilmay qolishi jamiyat uchun ham, shaxsning o'zi uchun ham jiddiy yo'qotish bo'lmagani holda, biror ma'naviy qadriyat, axloqiy sifatni o'zlashtirmagani chinakam fojia ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. Adabiyotshunos o'z fikrini yanada rivojlantirib: "Pifagor teoremasi yoki suvning formulasini bilganda ham,

bilmaganda ham kishining, uni o‘rab turgan olamning mohiyati o‘zgarishsiz qolaveradi. Lekin hazrati Navoiyning: “Lolazor ermashki, ohimdin jahonga tushdi o‘t, Yo‘q shafaqkim, bir qiroqdin osmonga tushdi o‘t” matla‘li yoki: “Meni men istagan o‘z suhbatiga arjmand etmas, Meni istar kishining suhbatin ko‘nglim pisand etmas” misralari bilan boshlanadigan g‘azallarining badiiy jozibasi va mantiqiy qudratini his etgan odam uchun olam ham, odamlar ham, hayot ham boshqacharoq bo‘lib qolishi aniq. Bulardan bexabar odamning ruhiyatida muayyan kemtiklik bo‘lishi shubhasizdir. Demak, asl badiiy asar odamning o‘zida, uning tabiatida, manaviyatida ma‘lum yangilanish, evrilish sodir qiladi”¹³. [1, 19-b]

Olim yangi metodologik qarashlarga ehtiyoj kuchli bo‘lgani holda, hanuz uning yetakchi belgilari muayyanlashmaganligini uqtiradi. Q.Yo‘ldoshev adabiyotshunoslar diqqatini badiiy so‘zning o‘ziga qaratish, ehtirosli munosabatlarni vazmin va salmoqdor tadqiqotlar hisobiga bartaraf qilishga intiladi. Chunki badiiy adabiyotni qiyofasi o‘zgargan zamon va sog‘lom tafakkur nuqtai nazaridan o‘qish, idrok etish, tushunish va tahlil etish masalasi o‘z yechimini kutayotgan dolzarb muammolardan biridir. Shunday ekan, adabiyotshunos olimlarimiz va munaqqidlarimizning o‘z qarashlarini belgilab, tahlil va talqin tamoyillarini aniqlab olishga kirisha boshlashlari ma‘qul bo‘lib, bu paydo bo‘lgan yangicha fikrlash ilmiy tadqiqotning mutlaqo yangi nazariy asoslarini shakllantirish zarurati tufayli ekanligi ayonlashadi.

Biroq mazkur anglash jarayoni birdaniga va oson bo‘ladi, deb o‘ylash noto‘g‘ri, chunki adabiyotni ijtimoiy hodisa deb bilgan va murosasiz munozaralarga ko‘nikkan ayrim tadqiqotchilar butun umr tayanib, ishonib kelgan qarashlari keraksiz ekanligiga ishonishi qiyin bo‘lishi, shu bois ayrim adabiyotshunos olimlar adabiy-estetik hodisalarga haligacha o‘jarlik bilan eski qoliplaridan foydalanib yondashaverishlari, yangicha tafakkur maromini topa olmayotganlari ham haqiqat ekanligi olim tadqiqotlarida aks etgan.

Q.Yo‘ldoshev “Haqiqiy badiiyat, anglangan va anglatilgan go‘zallik kitobxonning nafaqat ma‘naviyati, balki tafakkuriga ham ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi, uning shaxs sifatida shakllanish jarayoniga to‘g‘ri yo‘nalish beradi”,- deb hisoblaydi. Chindan ham badiiy adabiyotni faqat hayotiy savollarga javob beradigan, o‘quvchilarni yashashga o‘rgatadigan amaliy vosita tarzida tushunish noto‘g‘ridir. Chunki badiiy adabiyot savollarga javob bermaydi, balki kitobxon oldiga savollar qo‘yish yo‘li bilan unda ma‘naviy-fikriy munosabat uyg‘otadi. Bu munosabat oldin adabiy qahramonlarga yo‘naltirilgan bo‘lsa, keyinchalik, birinchi navbatda, o‘quvchining o‘ziga qaratiladi. Demak, anglangan badiiyat o‘quvchini o‘ylashga, o‘ylanishga o‘rgatadi. Shuningdek, adabiyot u yoki bu tarzda yashash kerak deb o‘quvchiga yo‘l ham ko‘rsatmaydi. Chunki har bir insonning xarakteri har xil, u tushishi mumkin bo‘lgan hayotiy vaziyatlarning bir-biridan keskin farq qiladi, tavsiya berishning imkoni yo‘q.

Yangicha adabiy qarashlarning shakllanishida A.Quljonov, A.Kattabekov, U.O‘ljaboyev, R.Majidov, V.Rahmonov, Q.Yo‘ldoshev, M.Mamatqulov kabi adabiyotshunos va metodist olimlarning o‘rni alohida bo‘lib, bu ularning adabiyotshunolikka doir adabiy-estetik, tanqidiy-ilmiy qarashlarida, ijodiy yo‘nalishlarlarida, ilmiy tafakkurdagi mushtarak jihatlar ifodasida ko‘rinadi.

Q.Yo‘ldoshev badiiy asarning tahlili butun adabiy ta‘limni boshqarishi, adabiy ta‘lim orqali esa butun millatni boshqarishiga to‘xtaladi. Umuman, 1980-yillardan boshlab, o‘zbek millatining ijtimoiy hayoti va taraqqiyotida asar tahlilining katta ahamiyatga egaligi anglashila boshlandi. Kitobxon, ayniqsa, filologlar badiiy asarlarni tahlil etish yo‘l-yo‘rig‘ini fan darajasida o‘rganmas va har qanday janrdagi asarni tahlil qila olish malakasiga ega bo‘lmas ekan, adabiy ta‘limdan kuzatilgan maqsad to‘liq amalga oshmasligi, adabiyot

¹³ O‘sha kitob. – B. 19.

o'qituvchisi nochorligicha, adabiyot darslari zerikarliligicha, asardan chiqariladigan xulosa "ijtimoiy nasihat"ligicha qolaverishi olim tomonidan ta'kidlanadi. Tahlillar g'arib bo'lganligi uchun adabiyot o'qitish jarayoni oldiga qo'yilgan bosh maqsad – barkamol shaxs shakllantirishga erishilmaydi, uning o'rniga quruq chaqiriq va yoqimsiz nasihatbozlik bilan o'quvchilarni haqiqiy adabiyotdan bezdirish yuzaga keladi va ularning ma'naviyatini qashshoqlashtirish davom etaveradi.

Badiiy asarni tahlil qilish malakasiga yetarlicha ega bo'lmagan mutaxassis talabalarga nima "berish"ni bilmaganidek, ulardan nimani "talab etish"ni ham tasavvur qilolmaydi. Shu bois, adabiyot darslarida talabalar zimmasiga g'oyat yengil va keraksiz "yuk" qo'yiladi. Yengil-yelpi, talabalarning xayolotini ishga solmaydigan, aqlini zo'riqtirmaydigan "javob"lar adabiyot bo'yicha ijobiy baho olish uchun yetarli hisoblanib kelinadi.

"Badiiy asar matni bilan ishlashni o'z faoliyatining markaziy masalasi deb hisoblamaydigan adabiy ta'lim avval boshdan muvaffaqiyatsizlikka mahkumdur. Badiiy tahlilsiz adabiy ta'lim ma'naviyatsiz shaxs, bilimsiz mutaxassis demakdir. Yangilangan milliy pedagogika o'z oldiga ma'naviyati yuksak shaxslarni shakllantirish maqsadini qo'ygan ekan, adabiy ta'limda badiiy tahlil hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lishi shubhasizdir. Malakali badiiy tahlil bo'lmagan joyda mo'jizaviy asarning sehri, siri, jozibasi yo'qqa chiqadi. Chunki uning zamiridagi badiiy va hayotiy ma'no payqalmay qolaveradi. Adabiyot o'qitishda badiiy tahlilga e'tibor g'oyat sust bo'lganligi uchun ham millat ahlining bir necha avlodi Navoiy, Bobur, Mashrab va Qodiriysiz yashab kelmoqda. Chunki o'zbek adabiyotshunosligi va adabiyot o'qitish metodikasida ijodkorlarning asarlariga xos badiiy jihatlarni butun ko'lami, barcha qirralari bilan aniqlash hamda talaba va o'quvchilarga yetkazib berish mexanizmi ishlab chiqilgani yo'q".[1, 20-b]

Q.Yo'ldoshev "Alpomish" dostoniga ham aynan o'zbek millatiga xos bo'lgan jihatlarni aniqlash uchungina yondashgani asar bilan tanishgan o'quvchiga darhol ayon bo'ladi. Olim dostonni tekshirishda milliy o'ziga xoslikdangina kelib chiqqan, jahon folklorida mavjud dostonlar bilan syujeti o'xshashligi kabi omillarga chalg'imag, aynan o'zbek millatiga xos alomatlarinigina topgan. Olimning fikricha, har bir badiiy asarda, u aniq bir milliy zaminda paydo bo'lganligi uchun, o'sha sharoitgagina tegishli bo'lgan jihatlarning izi qoladi. Bunday belgilar har doim ham yarq etib ko'zga tashlanib turavermaydi. Ba'zi asarlarda butun asar yo'nalishini belgilab turadigan darajada kuchli bo'lsa, ba'zi asarlarda ko'zga tashlanmaydigan darajada sezilmas bo'ladi. Demak, o'sha asarni tekshirish va tahlil qilishda ham asar yaratilgan joyga, o'sha yerlik odamlarning dunyoqarashiga xos xususiyatlar aniq hisobga olinishi lozim.

Yangicha qarashlar shakllanishida Sirdaryo adabiyotshunoslik va metodik maktablarining asoschilaridan bo'lgan Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshevning hissasi beqiyosdir. Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshev serqirra ijodkor sifatida xalq og'zaki ijodi, mumtoz adabiyot, tilshunoslik, adabiyot o'qitish metodikasi, istiqloq davri o'zbek adabiyoti, adabiyotshunoslikning nazariy masalalari, modern va postmodern adabiyot kabi soha va yo'nalishlar bo'yicha chuqur ilmiy tahlillar olib borganligi buni dalolatlaydi. **Olimning adabiyotshunoslik badiiy asarda tasvirlangan alohida shaxs ko'nglidagi ruhiy tovlanishlarning ildizlarini topa bilgandagina chinakam ilmiy xulosalar chiqara olishi, bu yo'lda ba'zan u ijodkorning o'zi ham sezmagani jihatlarni kashf etishi, asarning yashirin qatlamlarini ko'ra bilishi mumkinligi, teran ilmiy kuzatishlarga boy adabiyotshunoslik millatning umumiy saviyasiga ta'sir ko'rsata olishi, mulohazali o'quvchilarni tarbiyalashi haqidagi fikrlari alohida ahamiyatga molik. Mazkur qarashlardan adabiyotshunoslikning rivoj topishi millatning ham rivojlanishiga zamin bo'lishi mumkinligi xususida xulosa ham kelib chiqqan.**

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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PEDAGOGIK TERMINLAR UYADOSHLIK LUG'ATI VA UNING ELEKTRON PLATFORMASINI YARATISHNING LINGVISTIK ASOSLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada pedagogik terminologiyaning tizimli tahlili va uyadoshlik tamoyillari asosida lug'at yaratishning nazariy-amaliy jihatlari o'rganilgan. Pedagogik terminlarning morfologik, semantik va etimologik jihatdan guruhlash tamoyillari, ularning o'zaro bog'liqligi va tizimli munosabatlari tahlil qilingan. Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari asosida elektron lug'at platformasini yaratishning lingvistik asoslari, uning struktur-funksional xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchilarga qulaylik yaratish imkoniyatlari ko'rsatilgan. Tadqiqot davomida pedagogik terminlarning so'z yasash modellari, ularning paradigmatic va sintagmatik munosabatlari, shuningdek, terminologik uyadoshlikning kog'nitiv-onomasiologik asoslari ochib berilgan. Elektron platformaning interfeysi, qidiruv tizimi va ma'lumotlar bazasini tashkil etish prinsiplari ilmiy asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik terminologiya, uyadoshlik lug'ati, elektron platforma, terminologik sistema, so'z yasash, semantik maydon, leksikografiya, korpus lingvistikasi, terminosistema, axborot texnologiyalari.

Pedagogik terminologiya zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ta'lim jarayonidagi barcha hodisa va tushunchalarni ifodalash vositasi hisoblanadi. Pedagogika fani rivojlanib borishi bilan uning terminologik apparati ham boyib, murakkablashib bormoqda. Shu munosabat bilan pedagogik terminlarni tizimli ravishda o'rganish, ularning o'zaro munosabatlarini aniqlash va uyadoshlik tamoyillari asosida lug'at yaratish dolzarb masalaga aylanmoqda.

Uyadoshlik lug'ati tushunchasi zamonaviy leksikografiyada muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu turdagi lug'atlar so'zlarni tasodifiy emas, balki ularning ichki bog'liqligi, so'z yasash munosabatlari va semantik yaqinligi asosida guruhlab beradi. Pedagogik terminlar maydonida bunday lug'at yaratish nafaqat nazariy, balki amaliy ahamiyatga ham ega, chunki u talabalar, o'qituvchilar va tadqiqotchilar uchun terminologik apparatni tizimli o'zlashtirish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Pedagogik terminlarning uyadoshlik asosida tashkil etilishi so'z yasash qonuniyatlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq. O'zbek tilida pedagogik terminlar asosan uch yo'l bilan hosil bo'ladi: morfologik usul orqali, sintaktik birikishlar orqali va leksik-semantik o'zgarishlar natijasida. Morfologik usulda qo'shimchalar yordamida hosil bo'lgan terminlar alohida e'tiborga sazovordir. Masalan, "ta'lim" ildizidan "ta'limli", "ta'limsiz", "ta'limchi", "ta'limgoh", "ta'limiy" kabi uyadosh terminlar hosil bo'ladi. Bu terminlar bir-biri bilan morfologik va semantik jihatdan bog'liq bo'lib, umumiy ildizga ega.

Terminologik uyadoshlik tushunchasini to'g'ri tushunish uchun uning lingvistik asoslarini chuqur o'rganish zarur. Uyadoshlik nafaqat so'z yasash munosabatlarini, balki

semantik maydonlar, leksik-semantik guruhlar va terminologik mikrotizimlardagi o'zaro bog'liqliklarni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Pedagogik terminologiyada "o'qitish" tushunchasi atrofida shakllangan terminlar uyasi bu hodisaning yaqqol namunasidir. "O'qitish", "o'qituvchi", "o'qitiluvchi", "o'quv", "o'quvchi", "o'qish" kabi terminlar nafaqat so'z yasalish jihatidan, balki semantik jihatdan ham bir-biriga bog'liq.

Pedagogik terminlarning etimologik tahlili ham uyadoshlik lug'atini yaratishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. O'zbek pedagogik terminologiyasida so'z boyligining turli qatlamlari mavjud: o'zbek tilining o'z so'zlari, arabo-fors tillari orqali kirib kelgan so'zlar va rus tili orqali kirgan xalqaro terminlar. Har bir qatlam o'zining uyadosh terminlar guruhini hosil qiladi. Masalan, "maktab" arabcha asosidan "maktabchi", "maktabdosh", "maktabgacha", "maktabdan tashqari" kabi terminlar hosil bo'lgan.

Semantik maydonlar nazariyasi pedagogik terminlarning uyadoshlik asosida guruhlanishida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Pedagogik terminologiya bir nechta yirik semantik maydonlarga bo'linadi: ta'lim jarayoni, tarbiya jarayoni, ta'lim mazmuni, ta'lim shakllari, ta'lim metodlari, ta'lim vositalari va boshqalar. Har bir semantik maydon ichida kichik semantik guruhlar va terminologik uyalar shakllanadi. Masalan, "metod" terminining atrofida "metodika", "metodolog", "metodist", "metodologiya", "metodlar tizimi" kabi uyadosh terminlar to'plami mavjud.

Pedagogik terminlarning paradigmatic munosabatlari ham uyadoshlik lug'ati uchun muhim parametrdir. Bu munosabatlar sinonimiya, antonimiya, giperonimiya-giponimiya va boshqa semantik munosabatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Masalan, "o'qitish usuli" giperonimining "ma'ruza", "suhbat", "munozara", "amaliy mashg'ulot" kabi giponimlar uyasi pedagogik terminologiyaning muhim qismidir. Bu turdagi munosabatlarni aks ettirish lug'atning ilmiy qiymatini oshiradi.

Pedagogik terminlarning sintagmatik munosabatlari ularning nutqda qo'llanilishi, boshqa so'zlar bilan birikish qobiliyati bilan bog'liq. Ko'pgina pedagogik terminlar barqaror birikmalar tarkibida ishlatiladi va bu birikishlar ham terminologik uyalarning bir qismini tashkil etadi. "Ta'lim" so'zi "ta'lim jarayoni", "ta'lim tizimi", "ta'lim mazmuni", "ta'lim shakllari" kabi ko'plab barqaror birikmalar hosil qiladi va bu birikmalarning har biri alohida termin sifatida qaralishi mumkin. Zamonaviy leksikografiyada elektron lug'atlar an'anaviy qog'oz lug'atlarga nisbatan qator ustunliklarga ega. Elektron lug'atlar operativ qidiruv imkoniyatini beradi, dinamik yangilanishi mumkin, multimediya imkoniyatlaridan foydalanadi va foydalanuvchilarga interaktiv ish rejimini taklif qiladi. Pedagogik terminlar uyadoshlik lug'atining elektron platformasini yaratish bu ustunliklardan to'liq foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Elektron platformaning lingvistik asoslari lug'atning strukturasi belgilaydi. Platforma uch asosiy komponentdan iborat bo'lishi kerak: ma'lumotlar bazasi, qidiruv tizimi va foydalanuvchi interfeysi. Ma'lumotlar bazasi barcha pedagogik terminlarni ularning to'liq tavsifi bilan saqlaydi. Har bir termin uchun quyidagi ma'lumotlar kiritiladi: termin shakli, ta'rifi, etimologiyasi, so'z yasalish tuzilishi, sinonim va antonimlari, qo'llanish misollari va uyadosh terminlar ro'yxati.

Terminlarni ma'lumotlar bazasida tashkil etish prinsipi juda muhimdir. Har bir termin alohida ob'ekt sifatida saqlanadi va uning barcha atributlari va boshqa terminlar bilan bog'liqlik munosabatlari bazada aks ettiriladi. Bu relatsion ma'lumotlar bazasi printsipiga asoslanadi. Terminlar orasidagi munosabatlar turli xil bo'lishi mumkin: so'z yasalish munosabatlari, semantik munosabatlar, paradigmatic munosabatlar va boshqalar. Har bir munosabat turi ma'lumotlar bazasida alohida jadval orqali ifodalanadi.

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PEDAGOGIK TERMINLAR UYADOSHLIK LUG'ATINING ELEKTRON PLATFORMASI

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Annotatsiya: Qidiruv tizimi elektron lug'atning eng muhim funksional komponentidir. Foydalanuvchi turli parametrlar bo'yicha qidiruv amalga oshirishi mumkin bo'lishi kerak. Eng oddiy qidiruv - bu termini to'g'ridan-to'g'ri kiritish orqali qidirish. Ammo bundan tashqari, qo'shimcha qidiruv imkoniyatlari ham bo'lishi zarur: ildiz bo'yicha qidiruv, semantik maydon bo'yicha qidiruv, so'z turkumi bo'yicha qidiruv, etimologiya bo'yicha qidiruv va boshqalar. Ildiz bo'yicha qidiruv foydalanuvchiga ma'lum bir ildizga mansub barcha uyadosh terminlarni bir vaqtning o'zida ko'rish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik, terminlar, uyadoshlik, lug'at, elektron, platforma, lingvistik, asoslar.

Interfeys foydalanuvchilarga qulay va intuitiv bo'lishi kerak. Asosiy sahifada qidiruv maydoni va terminlar ro'yxati joylashadi. Terminlar ro'yxati alifbo tartibida yoki tematik guruhlar bo'yicha tartiblanishi mumkin. Har bir termini tanlash uning to'liq tavsifiga olib boradi. Tavsif sahifasida terminning barcha lingvistik xususiyatlari, qo'llanish misollari va uyadosh terminlar uyasi ko'rsatiladi. Uyadosh terminlar uyasi vizual sxema ko'rinishida taqdim etilishi mumkin, bu foydalanuvchiga terminlar orasidagi bog'liqliklarni yaqqol ko'rish imkonini beradi.

Pedagogik terminlar uyadoshlik lug'atining elektron platformasi uchun terminlarni tanlash va ularga tavsif berish maxsus metodologiyani talab qiladi. Birinchidan, pedagogik terminlarning to'liq korpusini to'plash zarur. Bu korpus pedagogika bo'yicha darsliklar, qo'llanmalar, ilmiy maqolalar va dissertatsiyalar asosida shakllantiriladi. Korpus lingvistikasi metodlari yordamida terminlarning qo'llanish chastotasi, kontekstual xususiyatlari va boshqa statistik ko'rsatkichlari aniqlanadi.

Terminlarga tavsif berish uchun maxsus metama'lumotlar tizimi ishlab chiqiladi. Har bir termin uchun quyidagi metama'lumotlar to'planadi: fonetik shakl, morfologik tuzilish, so'z turkumi, so'z yasaliş usuli, ildiz va qo'shimchalar, semantik tavsif, ta'rif, sinonim va antonimlar, giperonimlar va giponimlar, kontekstual qo'llanish xususiyatlari, chastota ko'rsatkichi, etimologik ma'lumot, tarjimalar va ekvivalentlar boshqa tillarda. Bu metama'lumotlar tizimi lug'atning ilmiy qiymatini ta'minlaydi va turli xil qidiruv imkoniyatlarini yaratadi.

Terminologik uyalarni aniqlash va tasvirlash maxsus algoritmlar asosida amalga oshiriladi. So'z yasaliş uyalari morfologik tahlil algoritmlari yordamida aniqlanadi. Bu algoritmlar terminlarni ildiz va qo'shimchalarga ajratadi va bir xil ildizga ega bo'lgan terminlarni bir uyaga birlashtiradi. Semantik uylar esa semantik tahlil va terminlar o'rtasidagi ma'no munosabatlarini aniqlash orqali shakllantiriladi. Buning uchun zamonaviy kompyuter lingvistikasi va sun'iy intellekt metodlaridan foydalaniladi.

Elektron platformaning arxitekturasi zamonaviy veb-texnologiyalar asosida quriladi. Platforma kliyent-server arxitekturasiga ega bo'lib, server tomonda ma'lumotlar bazasi va biznes-logika, kliyent tomonda esa foydalanuvchi interfeysi joylashadi. Ma'lumotlar bazasi uchun relatsion ma'lumotlar bazasi boshqaruv tizimlari qo'llaniladi. Server tomondagi dasturiy ta'minot zamonaviy veb-freymvorklar yordamida ishlab chiqiladi va RESTful API orqali kliyent bilan muloqot qiladi.

Foydalanuvchi interfeysi responsiv dizayn printsipiga asoslanadi va turli xil qurilmalarda - kompyuter, planshet va smartfonlarda qulay ishlaydi. Interfeys dizayni zamonaviy UX/UI dizayn prinsiplariga muvofiq ishlab chiqiladi. Asosiy e'tibor qidiruv funksiyasining samaradorligi va ma'lumotlarning tushunarli taqdim etilishiga qaratiladi. Interfeys ko'p tilliligini ta'minlash ham muhim talabdir, chunki bu pedagogik terminlarning boshqa tillardagi ekvivalentlari bilan ishlash imkonini beradi.

Vizualizatsiya vositalari elektron lug'atning muhim qismidir. Terminologik uyalarni grafik sxemalar, daraxt strukturalari yoki tarmoq grafiklari ko'rinishida tasvirlash foydalanuvchilarga terminlar orasidagi munosabatlarni intuitiv tushunish imkonini beradi. Har bir terminning uyasi alohida sahifada vizual grafik sifatida taqdim etilishi mumkin, bu yerda markazda asosiy termin turadi va undan uyadosh terminlarga yo'naltirilgan strelkalar chiqadi. Har bir strelka munosabat turini ko'rsatadi: so'z yasaliş, sinonimiya, antonimiya va boshqalar.

Elektron platformaning qo'shimcha funksiyalari foydalanuvchilarga qo'shimcha qulayliklar yaratadi. Masalan, terminlarni qiyoslash funksiyasi ikki yoki undan ortiq terminning xususiyatlarini parallel ravishda ko'rish imkonini beradi. Shaxsiy kabinet

funksiyasi foydalanuvchilarga o'z sevimli terminlari ro'yxatini yaratish, qaydlar yuritish va terminlarni o'rganish jarayonini boshqarish imkonini beradi. Test va mashqlar bo'limi pedagogik terminlarni o'zlashtirish jarayonini faollashtiradi.

Pedagogik terminlar korpusini shakllantirishda maxsus e'tibor berilishi kerak bo'lgan jihatlari mavjud. Korpusga nafaqat standart va keng tarqalgan terminlar, balki yangi paydo bo'layotgan terminlar, neoterminlar ham kiritilishi kerak. Pedagogika fani rivojlanishi bilan yangi tushunchalar va terminlar paydo bo'lmoqda: onlayn ta'lim, masofaviy ta'lim, STEM ta'limi, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, inklyuziv ta'lim va boshqalar. Bu terminlarning ham o'z uyadosh terminlar uyalarini shakllanib bormoqda.

Terminologik standartlashtirish muammolari ham e'tiborga olinishi kerak. O'zbek pedagogik terminologiyasida ba'zi tushunchalar uchun bir nechta parallel terminlar mavjud bo'lishi mumkin. Lug'at yaratishda qaysi variant asosiy, qaysi variant sinonim ekanligi aniq belgilanishi zarur. Bu borada davlat standartlari, ta'lim vazirligi hujjatlari va nufuzli ilmiy manbalardan foydalaniladi. Standartlashtirilgan terminlar asosiy variant sifatida, boshqa variantlar sinonim sifatida ko'rsatiladi.

Mobil ilovalar zamonaviy foydalanuvchilar uchun qulay kirish yo'lini ta'minlaydi. Pedagogik terminlar lug'atining mobil versiyasi asosiy funksiyalarning barchasini o'z ichiga olishi va offline rejimda ishlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak. Mobil ilova ovoqli qidiruv, push-bildirishnomalar va boshqa mobil qurilmalarga xos funksiyalardan foydalanishi mumkin. Terminlarning audio talaffuzi ham mobil foydalanuvchilar uchun foydali xususiyatdir.

Elektron platformaning ochiq API interfeysi uchinchi tomon dasturchilariga lug'at ma'lumotlaridan foydalangan holda o'z ilovalarini yaratish imkonini beradi. Bu pedagogik terminologiya sohasida innovatsion yechimlar paydo bo'lishiga yordam beradi. API orqali boshqa ta'lim platformalari, masalan, onlayn ta'lim tizimlari yoki elektron darsliklar lug'at funksiyasidan foydalanishlari mumkin.

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CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES ONLINE IN INDEPENDENT STUDY

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Abstract. This article explores the challenges and strategies of distance language learning in the context of independent study, focusing on teaching foreign language online. The rapid development of digital technologies has created new opportunities for learners to access educational materials and practice language skills autonomously. However, independent online learning also brings difficulties such as reduced motivation, lack of feedback, limited speaking practice, and the challenge of maintaining discipline. Drawing on recent studies in computer-assisted language learning (CALL), learner autonomy, and online pedagogy, this research highlights effective strategies for overcoming these issues. Recommendations include integrating interactive platforms, providing structured self-study tasks, encouraging peer collaboration, and using adaptive assessment tools. The study concludes that successful independent online learning requires a balanced approach that combines technological resources with pedagogical support and learner self-regulation.

Keywords: distance learning, independent study, online foreign language teaching, learner autonomy, CALL.

Introduction. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the global transition to distance education, making online learning the primary mode of instruction in many contexts. While online platforms provide flexibility, accessibility, and a wealth of resources, the shift to independent study has placed additional responsibilities on learners. In foreign language learning, particularly foreign language, the challenge is compounded by the need for constant interaction, feedback, and practice of speaking and listening skills.

Independent online learning requires learners to demonstrate autonomy, motivation, and effective time management. For educators, the question is not only how to design engaging online materials, but also how to foster learner self-regulation and provide support without physical presence. This article examines the challenges associated with online foreign language learning in independent study and suggests strategies to overcome them.

Literature Review. Research on distance education emphasizes learner autonomy as a key factor for success (Holec, 1981; Little, 1991). Autonomous learners are able to set goals, monitor progress, and evaluate outcomes. However, in practice, not all students possess the skills required for effective self-directed learning.

Recent studies on online learning (Hodges et al., 2020) indicate that the sudden shift to distance education during the pandemic revealed gaps in student preparedness for independent study. Issues such as screen fatigue, lack of real-time feedback, and unequal access to technology continue to challenge both learners and educators.

Methodology. The study adopts a qualitative approach based on analysis of existing research, online teaching practices, and case studies from language classrooms. The focus is placed on identifying key difficulties encountered by students in independent online study and the strategies educators have used to mitigate them. Data includes published studies in CALL, online pedagogy, and language teaching methodology.

Results and Discussion. The analysis of distance language learning in the context of independent study reveals a complex combination of opportunities and challenges that directly influence the effectiveness of foreign language online teaching. One of the central issues is reduced motivation: in the absence of live classroom interaction, many learners struggle to maintain consistent interest and commitment to their studies. This problem is closely connected with another difficulty, the lack of timely feedback, particularly in the development of oral skills. Independent online environments often provide abundant reading and writing tasks, yet they rarely guarantee sufficient opportunities for speaking and listening practice, which are essential for communicative competence. At the same time, the burden of self-regulation and discipline becomes heavier in the online mode, where the responsibility for following a learning plan rests almost entirely on the learner. Procrastination, irregular study habits, and ineffective time management are among the most common barriers encountered in this context.

Technological limitations further complicate the process. Unequal internet access, technical malfunctions, and insufficient digital literacy prevent students from fully benefiting from the available resources. Despite these obstacles, independent online learning also opens new possibilities. Learners gain access to interactive platforms that enable vocabulary expansion, grammar practice, and immediate automated assessment. Virtual speaking clubs, discussion forums, and peer collaboration initiatives help mitigate the sense of isolation and create conditions for social learning. Moreover, structured self-study programs designed by teachers provide an essential framework that prevents learners from being overwhelmed by excessive freedom and lack of direction. Adaptive assessment tools, supported by artificial intelligence, allow students to monitor their progress in real time and receive feedback that encourages further development.

Overall, the results suggest that the effectiveness of independent online language learning depends on a delicate balance between learner autonomy and external pedagogical support. When students are left entirely on their own, motivation and discipline quickly decline, while an excess of external control undermines the very concept of independent study. Therefore, the optimal approach is to integrate technological resources with carefully designed pedagogical guidance, ensuring that learners remain engaged, responsible, and

motivated, while still benefiting from the flexibility and accessibility that online education provides.

Pedagogical Implications. Teachers must balance autonomy with guidance, ensuring that students are not overwhelmed by the responsibility of independent learning. Training students in self-regulation and digital literacy is as important as teaching language skills themselves.

Conclusion. Independent online language learning offers both opportunities and challenges. While students gain flexibility and access to vast resources, they also face motivational, disciplinary, and interactive difficulties. Effective strategies include structured learning plans, interactive platforms, peer collaboration, and adaptive feedback. Ultimately, successful online learning requires a synergy between learner autonomy and teacher support. Future research should explore the long-term impact of independent online study on language proficiency and investigate how artificial intelligence tools can personalize feedback and foster oral communication in digital environments.

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QAHRAMON OBRAZINI YARATISHNING LISONIY VOSITASI.

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Annotatsiya: Har qanday san'at asaridagi badiiy obrazning asosiy predmeti bosh qahramon obrazi bo'lib, unga muallif turli xil stilistik uslublardan foydalangan holda tashqi ko'rinish va xarakterning ma'lum xususiyatlarini beradi. Ushbu uslublar o'quvchilarga adabiy asar olamiga kirib borishga yordam beradi, muallifning bosh qahramonni ichki holati, his-tuyg'ulari, kayfiyati va harakatlariga oid maqsadini tushunishga yordam beradi. Markaziy qahramonlar haqida to'liq tushunchaga ega bo'lgan o'quvchi butun asar tushunchasiga chuqurroq kirib bora oladi. Ushbu maqolada qahramon obrazini yaratishning lisoniy vositalari misollar yordamida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: metonimiya, lisoniy vosita, obraz, antiteza, mubolag'a, metafora.

Annotation: The main subject of the literary image in any work of literature is the image of the main character, to which the author gives certain features of appearance and character using various stylistic methods. These techniques help readers to enter the world of the literary work, help to understand the purpose of the author regarding the inner state, feelings, mood and actions of the main character. A reader who has a complete understanding

of the central characters can go deeper into the concept of the whole work. In this article, the linguistic means of creating the image of the hero are explained with the help of examples.

Key words: metonymy, linguistic tool, image, antithesis, exaggeration, metaphor.

Аннотация: Основным предметом литературного образа в любом литературном произведении является образ главного героя, которому автор, используя различные стилистические приемы, придает определенные черты внешности и характера. Эти приемы помогают читателям войти в мир литературного произведения, помогают понять цель автора относительно внутреннего состояния, чувств, настроения и действий главного героя. Читатель, имеющий полное представление о центральных героях, может глубже проникнуть в концепцию всего произведения. В данной статье на примерах объясняются языковые средства создания образа героя.

Ключевые слова: метонимия, языковой инструмент, образ, антитеза, преувеличение, метафора.

Badiiy asar qahramoni hamma tomonlama haqiqiy odamdan ustundir. Masalan, asar qahramoni murakkab, o'zgaruvchan, ba'zan sirli bo'lishi mumkin, lekin u o'quvchiga doim tushunarli bo'lishi kerak. O'quvchi qahramon obrazini uning harakatlarini o'rgangandan so'ng, uning boshqa personajlar bilan yoki o'zi bilan munosabatlarini tahlil qilgandan so'ng o'z ongida shakllantiradi. Qolaversa, qahramonning xarakteri va qiyofasi tashqi xususiyatlar orqali va uning yaqinlari muhiti, unga tegishli narsalar orqali ochiladi. Qahramonning fikr va harakatlariga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

“Badiiy obraz har doim ham shaxsning umumlashtirilgan, tiplashtirilgan tasviri bo'lavermaydi. Badiiy asarda konkret shaxs va hodisalarni tasvirlash orqali butun bir davrning umumlashtirilgan obrazi, jamiyat yoki tabiat obrazi yaratilishi mumkin”. Qahramon obrazini yaratishning navbatdagi lisoniy vositasi metonimiyadir. Metonimiya muayyan ob'ekt yoki belgi haqidagi g'oyalarni kuchaytiradi va buni quyidagi misolda ko'rish mumkin:

But the other knight hit him so hard in midst of the shield, that horse and man fell to the earth, and therewith Arthur was eager, and pulled out his sword, and said, I will assay thee, sir knight, on foot, for I have lost the honour on horseback.

Tarjimasi: Va ritsar uning qalqoni o'rtasiga shunday kuch bilan urdiki, ot va chavandoz erga quladi. Shunda Artur g'azablanib, qilichini chiqarib dedi: "Endi men sizga piyoda hujum qilaman, ser ritsar, chunki men egarda qarshilik qila olmadim va mag'lub bo'ldim."

E'tiborli jihati shundaki, "Arturning o'limi" romanida badiiy obraz yaratish vositasi sifatida metonimiya nihoyatda kam uchraydi, "Qirol Xorn" romanida esa umuman yo'q.

Foydalanish darajasi bo'yicha metonimiya bilan bir qatorda antiteza mavjud. Antitezaning eng yorqin misoli quyidagilardir:

At that time came in the Knight with the Two Swords and his brother Balan, but they two did so marvellously that the king and all the knights marvelled of them, and all they that beheld them said they were sent from heaven as angels, or devils from hell...

Tarjimasi: Ikki qilichli ritsar akasi bilan u erga etib keldi va ikkalasi shunaqangi mo'jizalar ko'rsatdiki, qirol va barcha ritsarlar hayratda qolishdi. Ularni jangda ko'rgan har bir kishi, ular osmondan yuborilgan farishtalar yoki er osti dunyosidan kelgan shaytonlar bo'lsa kerak, deb aytishdi.

Garchi qirol va uning ritsarlari o'z davlatlarida eng kuchli va jasur bo'lsalar ham, ular bu ikki ritsar ularni mag'lub etganini tan olishadi, va bunda ularga faqat samoviy yoki shaytoniy kuchlar yordam berishi mumkinligiga ishora qiladi. Ehtimol, bu o'rinda muallif nafaqat jismoniy, balki butun ritsarlikning ma'naviy kuchini ham ko'rsatishga uringandir.

Har bir qahramonning o'ziga xosligi va individualligini ta'kidlash uchun muallif ko'pincha mubolag'adan foydalanadi. Quyida "Arturning o'limi" asaridagi mubolag'aga ayrim misollar keltirilgan.

...here lieth a duchess dead, the which was the fairest of all the world, wife to Sir Howell, Duke of Brittany, he hath murdered her in forcing her, and hath slit her unto the navel.

Tarjimasi: ... bu erda Bretani gertsogi, ser Xauelning rafiqasi, dunyoda go'zallikda tengi bo'lmagan, marhuma gertsoginya yotadi. Eri uni zo'ravonlik bilan o'ldirdi, va uni kindigigacha yirtib tashladi.

Bu o'rinda muallif nafaqat ayolning go'zalligini, balki qotilining shafqatsizligini ko'rsatmoqchi bo'lgan. Bu usul ayollarni himoya qilishga majbur bo'lgan ritsarlardan farqli o'laroq, qotilning asossizligini ta'kidlash uchun ishlatiladi.

But, sir, said the lady, as thou art called the worshipfullest knight of the world, I require thee of true knighthood, keep me and save me.

Tarjimasi: Oh, janob, - dedi xonim, - siz dunyodagi eng olijanob ritsar hisoblanasiz, men sizdan ritsarlik burchingizni o'rta qo'yib so'rayman - meni himoya qiling va qutqaring, chunki u sizga nima demasin, baribir meni o'ldiradi, chunki u shafqatsiz.

Bu misol, shuningdek, ba'zi qahramonlarning shafqatsizligi va boshqalarning olijanobligini ko'rsatadi va shu bilan ularni qarama-qarshi qo'yadi.

"Qirol Xorn" romanida ham mubolag'a mavjud:

Heo luvede so Horn child

That negh heo gan wexe wild:

For heo ne mighte at borde

With him speke no worde

Qirolning qizi Rimexild Xorning bo'lgan muhabbatdan "aqldan ozdi", bu qizning unga bo'lgan haqiqiy his-tuyg'ulari haqida gapiradi. Biroq, u hali ham qizning sevgisini qabul qila olmaydi, chunki u o'zga yurtda bo'lgani uchun past tabaqa vakili deb hisoblanardi. U qizning his-tuyg'ularini o'z maqsadlari yo'lida ishlata olmaydiki, bu ham uning olijanobligidan dalolat edi.

Yuqorida qayd etilgan lingvistik vositalardan tashqari, u yoki bu darajada qahramonlar obrazini yaratishga yordam beradigan boshqa vositalarni ham topdik. masalan, "Arturning o'limi" romanidagi ma'lum bir ma'noni anglatuvchi ismlarni olaylik: Sir Gilbert the Bastard (nikohsiz tug'ilgan), King Anguish of Scotland (bu ism qirolning fojiali taqdirini bildiradi) yoki podshohlarning jangchilari sonini ko'rsatishni olaylik:

The first that began the oath was the Duke of Cambenet, that he would bring with him five thousand men of arms... Then sware King Brandegoris of Stranggore that he would bring five thousand men of arms on horseback. Then sware King Clariance of Northumberland he would bring three thousand men of arms. Then sware the King of the Hundred Knights, that was a passing good man and a young, that he would bring four thousand men of arms on horseback. Then there swore King Lot, a passing good knight, and Sir Gawain's father, that he would bring five thousand men of arms on horseback. Also there swore King Urience, that was Sir Uwain's father, of the land of Gore, and he would bring six thousand men of arms on horseback. Also there swore King Idres of Cornwall, that he would bring five thousand men of arms on horseback. Also there swore King Cradelmas to bring five thousand men on horseback. Also there swore King Agwisance of Ireland to bring five thousand men of arms on horseback. Also there swore King Nentres to bring five thousand men of arms on horseback. Also there swore King Carados to bring five thousand men of arms on horseback.

Tarjimasi: Bu bayramga Lot va Orkney qiroli Lut va u bilan birga besh yuzta ritsar keldi; bayramga Gur yurtining qiroli Uriens ham keldi va u bilan birga to'rt yuzta ritsar bor

edi; qirol Garlota Kantr va u bilan etti yuzta ritsar keldi; shotlandiya qirol ham bu bayramga hali yosh bo'lsa-da, olti yuz ritsar bilan kelgan. Yana bir qirol etib keldi, u yuz ritsarli qirol deb atalgan, ammo uning o'zi va uning xalqi hamma narsada mukammal qurol va jihozlarga ega edi; qirol Karados ham yetib keldi va u bilan birga besh yuzta ritsar bor edi.

Ya'ni, qirolning qancha ko'p jangchisi bo'lsa, o'zi ham shunchalik kuchli va dono bo'ladi. Barcha lingvistik vositalarni o'rganib chiqib, ularni tahlil qilib, biz quyidagi xulosalarga keldik: ritsarlik romanining har bir muallifi o'ziga xos ritsarlik g'oyasiga va ritsarlar obrazlarini yaratishning o'ziga xos usullariga ega, chunki ikkita romanda biz asosiy tilshunoslikni tahlil qildik. Vositalari juda boshqacha – “Arturning o'limi” romanida bu mubolag'a va epiteta, “Qirol Xorn” romanida esa metafora va taqqoslash.

Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, ritsarlik romanlari mualliflari ko'pincha qahramonlarning ichki qiyofasini yoki tashqi ko'rinishini tasvirlashga murojaat qilmaydilar, aksincha, ko'p hollarda ular qahramonlarning xatti-harakatlari, nutqlari va his-tuyg'ularini aks ettiradilar. Ular uchun ritsarlarining jasorati va odilligi, ayollarning go'zalligi va nazokati, qirol va shahzodalarning kuch-qudrati, dushmanlarning zaif va qo'rqqoqligini o'z harakatlari va so'zlari bilan ko'rsatish muhimroqdir. Buning uchun ular turli stilistik vositalardan unumli foydalanganlar.

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CHALLENGES OF REMOTE LEARNING SYSTEMS AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR IMPROVEMENT

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Annotation: This article examines the core problems faced by remote learning systems and identifies practical strategies for improvement. The study highlights the most common issues, such as poor internet connectivity, insufficient digital resources, lack of motivation, limited teacher preparedness, and challenges in assessment and mental well-being. The article proposes several solutions including technological infrastructure development, innovative pedagogical approaches, teacher training, and psychological support for learners. The findings emphasize that a successful remote education system requires not only technological advancement but also human-centered strategies that ensure equity, engagement, and sustainability in the learning process.

Key words: Remote learning, online education, digital pedagogy, student motivation, teacher training, assessment, educational technology, distance education

Remote learning has become one of the most transformative trends in the global education system. It gained remarkable importance during the COVID-19 pandemic when educational institutions worldwide were forced to shift from traditional teaching to online

formats. While distance learning offers significant advantages such as flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility, it also introduces various challenges. The objective of this paper is to identify the main problems in remote learning systems and suggest effective ways to address them, focusing on the experience of higher education students in developing contexts like Uzbekistan.

A major obstacle is the unequal access to digital technologies. Many students lack reliable internet, modern computers, or smartphones capable of supporting online platforms. This “digital divide” results in unequal opportunities and learning outcomes among students from different regions or socioeconomic backgrounds.

Online environments can cause isolation and lack of concentration. Without in-person interaction and clear feedback, many students struggle to stay motivated. “Zoom fatigue” and the monotony of screen-based lessons often reduce active participation and academic performance.

Effective online teaching requires digital literacy and new pedagogical skills. However, many educators were not trained for virtual instruction and often transferred traditional classroom practices to online platforms without modification, leading to less effective learning experiences.

Monitoring academic honesty online is a serious issue. Students may use unauthorized resources during online assessments. Moreover, practical subjects-such as laboratory work or oral language activities-cannot be easily replicated through digital tools.

Continuous screen time, lack of face-to-face communication, and increased self-study responsibilities can cause stress, anxiety, and burnout. Social isolation further reduces students’ sense of belonging to the academic community

The efficiency of remote learning depends not only on technology but also on human adaptation. Motivation and interaction are central to successful online education. Universities should therefore focus on building virtual communities where both teachers and students feel connected and supported. Furthermore, investment in teacher training and institutional digital strategies is necessary to sustain long-term improvements.

Remote learning is an essential part of modern education that continues to evolve with technological and social changes. However, its success relies on solving the structural, pedagogical, and psychological challenges that hinder its quality and inclusiveness. To make remote education sustainable, educational institutions must strengthen digital infrastructure, ensure equal access, and promote interactive and student-centered teaching methods. Moreover, teachers must be continuously trained to apply innovative digital pedagogies that maintain engagement and academic integrity. When supported by effective policy, institutional collaboration, and technological investment, remote learning can become not merely an alternative mode of education but a powerful complement to traditional learning - fostering lifelong learning, flexibility, and global connectivity across all levels of education.

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DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION AND INCLUSIVE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article explores the concepts of Differentiated Instruction and Inclusive Teaching as essential approaches for creating equitable learning environments in modern education. It discusses the importance of recognizing students' diverse abilities, interests, and learning needs while designing lessons that provide multiple pathways for success. The paper also highlights practical strategies for implementing differentiated instruction in inclusive classrooms, the teacher's role in promoting equity, and the challenges faced in adapting traditional methods to meet all learners' needs.

Keywords: Differentiated instruction, inclusive education, diversity in the classroom, educational equity, learning needs, pedagogical approaches.

Education today demands flexibility, equality, and accessibility for every learner. As classrooms become increasingly diverse, teachers face the challenge of meeting a wide range of student needs. Differentiated instruction and inclusive teaching are pedagogical approaches designed to address this diversity, ensuring that every student, regardless of ability, background, or learning style, has the opportunity to succeed.

Definition of Differentiated Instruction

Differentiated instruction refers to the practice of tailoring teaching methods, learning activities, and assessment tools to accommodate the varied learning styles, interests, and readiness levels of students. According to Carol Ann Tomlinson, one of the pioneers in this field, differentiation means "providing multiple options for taking in information, making sense of ideas, and expressing what they learn."

Teachers can differentiate instruction through:

Content – varying what students learn;

Process – varying how they learn;

Product – varying how students demonstrate what they have learned;

Learning environment – creating supportive and flexible classroom settings.

Inclusive Teaching

Inclusive teaching ensures that all learners, including those with special educational needs, disabilities, or language barriers, are equally valued and given the opportunity to participate in the learning process. It goes beyond physical inclusion; it is about social, emotional, and academic inclusion.

Inclusive education promotes:

Respect for diversity;

Equal opportunities for participation;

Collaborative learning

The use of assistive technologies and adaptive materials.

The Relationship Between Differentiation and Inclusion

Differentiated instruction is a key strategy within inclusive education. Inclusion requires recognizing and responding to diversity, while differentiation provides the tools to do so effectively. Together, they ensure that education is fair, flexible, and student-centered.

For example, in an inclusive classroom, students with different learning abilities might be assigned tasks of varying complexity, while still working toward the same learning objectives. Visual aids, cooperative group work, and peer tutoring can help create an environment where every learner can thrive.

Practical Strategies

1. **Flexible Grouping:** Organizing students into small, dynamic groups based on skills or interests.
2. **Tiered Assignments:** Creating assignments with varying levels of difficulty to challenge all students appropriately.
3. **Choice Boards:** Allowing students to choose from multiple learning activities to suit their preferred learning style.
4. **Use of Technology:** Applying digital tools to personalize instruction and provide accessible materials.
5. **Formative Assessment:** Regularly assessing progress to adapt teaching to each learner's current needs.

Teacher's Role: The teacher acts as a facilitator who understands individual differences and designs lessons that meet each student's potential. They must demonstrate empathy, flexibility, and strong communication skills. Collaboration with parents, special educators, and psychologists is also crucial for effective inclusion.

Challenges and Solutions

Implementing differentiated and inclusive teaching faces several challenges such as large class sizes, limited resources, and lack of teacher training. However, professional development programs, administrative support, and collaborative teaching practices can significantly improve outcomes.

Conclusion

Differentiated instruction and inclusive teaching represent the future of education — an education system that values diversity and promotes equity. By adopting these approaches, educators can create classrooms that nurture every student's strengths, build confidence, and foster lifelong learning.

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CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ORAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. Teaching oral communication remains one of the most challenging aspects of foreign language education. While learners may acquire grammar and vocabulary through traditional methods, developing fluency, pronunciation, and interactive competence requires authentic practice and exposure. This article examines the key difficulties teachers face in teaching oral communication skills, including learner anxiety, limited classroom time, assessment issues, and lack of authentic contexts. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating communicative methodologies, task-based learning, and digital tools to overcome these challenges. The findings suggest that successful development of oral communication requires a balance between linguistic accuracy and communicative fluency, supported by learner-centered strategies.

Keywords: oral communication, speaking skills, foreign language teaching, communicative competence, classroom challenges.

Introduction. The development of oral communication skills is one of the most essential yet problematic areas in foreign language teaching. While written competence can be taught through exercises and controlled practice, speaking requires dynamic interaction, rapid processing, and confidence. For decades, teachers have acknowledged that helping students to speak fluently in a foreign language is far more challenging than teaching grammar or reading comprehension. In today's interconnected world, oral communication competence is no longer optional but a necessity. International mobility, global employment opportunities, and intercultural exchange make speaking skills a priority. However, learners often face psychological barriers such as fear of mistakes, anxiety about pronunciation, and lack of confidence in spontaneous conversation. Teachers, in turn, are constrained by limited classroom time, large group sizes, and the difficulty of creating authentic speaking contexts. This article addresses the main obstacles in teaching oral communication skills and explores pedagogical strategies that can enhance the effectiveness of instruction.

Literature Review. Research on oral communication in second and foreign language acquisition emphasizes its central role in communicative competence (Hymes, 1972). Canale and Swain (1980) identified speaking as an integral component of communicative competence alongside grammatical, sociolinguistic, and strategic elements. Richards (2008) highlighted that fluency is not only the ability to produce speech but also the capacity to interact effectively and spontaneously.

Scholars such as Horwitz (2001) have documented the pervasive issue of foreign language speaking anxiety, which negatively affects learner performance and willingness to communicate. Nation and Newton (2009) stressed the importance of fluency-oriented practice, while Thornbury (2005) argued for task-based approaches that simulate real-life communication.

More recent studies (Derwing & Munro, 2015; Rao, 2019) have focused on pronunciation instruction, advocating intelligibility over native-like accuracy. Digital technologies, such as speech recognition and virtual exchanges, have also emerged as tools to enhance oral communication practice in classroom and online settings.

Methodology. This study employs a qualitative approach through the review and analysis of existing research, teaching practices, and case studies in the field of foreign language pedagogy. Data sources include peer-reviewed articles, textbooks on communicative methodologies, and teacher-reported experiences. The methodology involves: identifying common challenges teachers encounter in teaching oral communication; categorizing these challenges into psychological, methodological, and contextual dimensions; evaluating existing strategies and innovations aimed at overcoming these challenges. This approach allows for a holistic understanding of the problem and provides a foundation for practical recommendations.

Results and Discussion. The findings indicate that teaching oral communication skills presents a set of interrelated challenges:

1. **Learner Anxiety and Psychological Barriers.** Students often hesitate to speak for fear of making mistakes or being judged. This anxiety reduces participation and limits opportunities for practice. Teachers need to create a supportive environment that encourages risk-taking and values communicative effort over perfection.

2. **Limited Classroom Time and Group Sizes.** Traditional classroom structures rarely allow sufficient speaking practice. Large groups reduce the teacher's ability to provide individual feedback, while limited lesson time often prioritizes grammar and vocabulary over speaking activities.

3. **Assessment Difficulties.** Evaluating oral performance is complex due to its subjective nature. Teachers struggle to balance criteria such as accuracy, fluency, pronunciation, and interaction. Overemphasis on accuracy may discourage students from speaking freely.

4. **Lack of Authentic Communication Contexts.** Classroom dialogues often feel artificial and fail to reflect real-life communicative demands. Without opportunities to use the language meaningfully, learners cannot transfer classroom skills to real situations.

5. **Potential Solutions: Communicative and Task-Based Approaches** (Role-plays, simulations, and problem-solving activities foster authentic interaction); **Integration of Technology** (Speech recognition apps, virtual exchanges, and online discussions extend speaking opportunities beyond the classroom); **Fluency over Perfection** (Prioritizing intelligibility and spontaneous expression reduces anxiety and builds confidence); **Learner-Centered Strategies** (Encouraging peer interaction, group work, and collaborative tasks promotes active engagement).

Conclusion. Teaching oral communication skills in foreign language classrooms is a demanding but essential endeavor. The main challenges – learner anxiety, time limitations, assessment difficulties, and lack of authentic contexts – require innovative pedagogical responses. By adopting communicative methodologies, integrating digital tools, and creating supportive learning environments, teachers can help learners develop both fluency and confidence. The future of foreign language education lies not in eliminating errors but in empowering students to communicate meaningfully across cultures.

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TA'LIM JARAYONIDA IJTIMOIIY-MADANIY YONDOSHUVNING MOHIYATI VA MAZMUNI

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Abstract: The article discusses a number of view points that contribute to students' cultural competence development. It examines a number of sosio-cultural competence, including independent educational activity, which determines the ability to practically reorganize activities, resulting in an interlingual and intercultural language personality.

Key words: educational-cognitive skills, approach to teaching, research activities, language and culture learning, cultural identification.

Ijtimoiy-madaniy yondashuv zamonaviy pedagogikaning ilmiy asosi sifatida shaxsni rivojlantirish va tarbiyalash muammolarini tadqiq qilishda, har qanday pedagogik hodisa va jarayonni ijtimoiy-madaniy tizimning elementlari sifatida ko'rib chiqish va ularni inson mavjudligining keng kontekstiga kiritish imkonini beradi. Ta'lim sohasida ro'y berayotgan o'zgarishlar inson hayotining barcha sohalarida kuzatilayotgan va pedagogik jarayonlar hamda hodisalarga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan global jarayonlarning bir qismidir, shuning uchun pedagogik muammolarni hal qilish, falsafiy va madaniy rejani tahlil qilish ahamiyatlidir. Ta'lim tizimining yangi paradigmaga o'tishi pedagogik madaniyat dinamikasini va o'qituvchi shaxsini muayyan ijtimoiy muhitga nisbatan o'zaro bog'lashni, bugungi kunda paydo bo'layotgan yangi pedagogika va pedagogik amaliyotni asoslashni talab qiladi.

Aynan shu omillar sabab, Xorijiy til fanining mazmunini jamiyat talablariga mos ravishda qayt isloh qilish zaruratini paydo qildi. Pedagogik faoliyat har doim ma'lum bir ijtimoiy-tarixiy va ijtimoiy-madaniy kontekstda yozilgan. O'qituvchi ma'lum bir ijtimoiy-madaniy tajribaning tashuvchisi sifatida ishlaydi, bu esa zamonaviy o'qituvchining kasbiy faoliyati haqida madaniy-pedagogik faoliyat sifatida fikr yuritish imkonini beradi.

Zamonaviy o'qituvchining kasbiga bunday qarash uning kasbiy tayyorgarligi jarayonida ijtimoiy-madaniy komponentga bo'lgan ehtiyojni belgilaydi. Shunday qilib, talabalarni pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash uning transformatsion funktsiyasini aks ettiruvchi ijtimoiy-madaniy tajribani rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi kerak. Zamonaviy jamiyatning pedagogik madaniyatidagi o'zgarishlarni hisobga olgan holda va ularning ma'nosini anglagan holda, o'qituvchi o'z kasbiy faoliyatini qayta tashkil etadi. Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiya zamonaviy o'qituvchining kasbiy mahoratining o'ziga xos belgisiga aylanadi, chunki u uni yangi pedagogik madaniyatning yaratuvchisi mavqeiga qo'yadi va shuning uchun talabalarni pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayonida ijtimoiy va madaniy masalalar ko'rsatilishi kerak.

Ijtimoiy-madaniy yondashuv o'qituvchini transformatsion faoliyatga yo'naltiradigan ijtimoiy va madaniy dasturlarni aks ettirishga imkon beradi. "Ijtimoiy-madaniy yondashuv" atamasi yaxlit xarakterli va ijtimoiy hodisalarni tushuntirishda ijtimoiy va madaniy sintez ma'nosini anglatadi. Tadqiqotchilarning qayd etishicha, jamiyatning har bir turi o'ziga xos madaniyat turiga ega bo'lib, u ma'lum bir dunyoqarashga asoslanadi. Ta'kidlanganidek, ijtimoiy va madaniy ijtimoiy-tarixiy borliqning tomonlari bo'lib, ularning o'zaro ta'siri dunyoni murakkab, tizimli ko'rish bilan tavsiflanadi.

Shaxs rivojlanishining ijtimoiy holatini tavsiflashda tashqi sharoitlarning ta'siri ta'kidlanadi, bu turli avlod maktab o'quvchilarining rivojlanishida yuzaga keladigan muammolarni tushuntirishga imkon beradi. Shaxsdagi bu xususiyatlar ta'lim va tarbiyaning yangi shakl va usullarini izlash zarurligini taqozo etadi. Pedagogik jarayonlarning mohiyati muammosini tahlil qilishda ma'lum xususiyatlarga bo'lgan ijtimoiy-madaniy talab

aniqlanadi. Mazkur tezis hulosasi sifatida shuni takidlash joizki, Chet tili daralarini tashkil etish jarayonda quyidagi ijtimoiy-madaniy xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqishni taklif qilamiz: shaxsni rivojlantirish yoki ijtimoiylashtirishga yo'naltirilganlik; reproduktiv yoki ijodiy faoliyatga e'tibor berish; ta'limning harakat mexanizmi (tarbiya-rivojlantirish yoki ta'limberilgan fazilatlarini shakllantirish); pedagogik jarayon ishtirokchilari o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir turi (avtoritar, manipulyativ, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi). Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, pedagogik bilimlarni o'zlashtirgan o'qituvchi va talaba (kulturologlarning fikriga ko'ra) turli xil ijtimoiy-madaniy "jamiyatlarda" bo'lib, vaqt chegaralari bilan ajralib turadi. O'qituvchilar turli avlod vakillari bo'lib, ular turli xil qadriyatlar, ideallar, an'analar, ijtimoiylik shakllari va boshqalar bilan ajralib turadi, ular tushunmovchilik, qarama-qarshilik, atrofdagi dunyoni idrok etishga, kasbiy me'yorlarga ishonmaslik holatlariga olib kelishi mumkin.

Demak, pedagogik ta'lim mazmunidagi ijtimoiy-madaniy yondashuv talabalarning hozirgi zamon jamiyatining pedagogik madaniyatiga qo'shilishi, uning muammolari va qarama-qarshiliklaridan xabardor bo'lishini belgilaydi. Ushbu yondashuv doirasidagi pedagogik faoliyat bakalavriat tomonidan qabul qilinadi ijtimoiy va madaniy faoliyat, ya'ni, har qanday turdagi ta'lim muassasalarida o'quv jarayoni bo'lajak o'qituvchini jamiyatning demokratik rivojlanish tendentsiyalarini hisobga olgan holda shaxsni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, darslarda o'qituvchi fanlararo aloqadorlikdan foydalanishi, o'quv fanlari mazmunini, o'zgaruvchan jamiyat muammolari hal etish yo'llarini izlab topishga o'rgatish lozim.

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THE ROLE OF GRAMMAR AND SYNTAX IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This research paper examines the essential role of grammar and syntax in the process of foreign language teaching and learning. Grammar provides the fundamental rules of language structure, while syntax determines how words and phrases are arranged to form meaningful sentences. The study analyzes the evolution of grammar teaching methods - from traditional rule-based instruction to communicative and task-based approaches. It highlights the importance of integrating grammar and syntax with communicative competence, emphasizing the role of context, interaction, and learner autonomy.

Keywords: grammar, syntax, language teaching, communicative approach, linguistic competence, digital pedagogy, second language acquisition

Introduction: Grammar and syntax form the intellectual foundation of every natural language. For teachers and learners alike, they are not merely sets of rules, but essential tools for expressing meaning, understanding context, and achieving fluency. Grammar defines the patterns that shape linguistic accuracy, while syntax determines how these patterns combine to create meaningful utterances. In traditional pedagogy, grammar teaching focused on correctness and memorization, often separating it from communicative practice. However, language is not static - it evolves through interaction. Therefore, the modern teacher must help learners use grammar dynamically and creatively, not mechanically. This article investigates how grammar and syntax should be taught in contemporary language classrooms. It also evaluates teaching strategies that integrate linguistic theory, practical communication, and technological innovation to achieve optimal learning outcomes.

Grammar is the set of structural rules that governs the composition of words, phrases, and sentences in a language. Syntax, a branch of grammar, studies the arrangement of words and their relationships within sentences.

Linguists like Noam Chomsky (1965) introduced the concept of Universal Grammar, suggesting that humans are born with an innate ability to acquire language. Michael Halliday (1978) emphasized the functional role of grammar, arguing that grammar should serve meaning and social interaction. These two perspectives - formal and functional - continue to shape grammar instruction today. In the classroom, understanding both perspectives enables teachers to design lessons that are analytical (rule-focused) yet practical (communication-based).

Evolution of grammar teaching methods: a. The Grammar-Translation Method. This method emphasized grammatical accuracy, translation, and rote memorization. Students learned rules deductively - from explanation to example - but communicative use was minimal.

b. The Direct and Audio-Lingual Methods

In the 20th century, methods shifted toward oral practice. The Audio-Lingual Method focused on repetition and habit formation, using drills to internalize structures. However, it lacked creativity and contextual relevance.

c. The Communicative Approach

Emerging in the 1970s, this approach transformed grammar teaching. Grammar was taught implicitly within communicative activities - dialogues, simulations, and role-plays. Learners were encouraged to focus on meaning before form.

d. Task-Based Learning (TBLT)

Introduced by Nunan (2004), this approach integrates grammar with purposeful communication. Learners complete real-world tasks, discovering grammatical rules through usage. This promotes autonomy and natural acquisition.

Syntax is central to producing meaningful and grammatically coherent speech. For example, changing the order of words can alter meaning entirely: The cat chased the mouse ≠ The mouse chased the cat. Therefore, syntactic awareness helps learners express nuances, build complex sentences, and improve comprehension.

Teachers can incorporate syntax teaching through:

Sentence-combining exercises to build complexity.

Error correction activities to enhance awareness.

Discourse-level grammar tasks, linking syntax with meaning and context. When students understand syntax as a meaning-making system rather than a set of rules, they become more confident and flexible communicators.

The cognitive approach views grammar learning as a process of mental pattern recognition. Learners notice, analyze, and internalize rules through exposure. Meanwhile, Vygotsky's sociocultural theory stresses that grammar develops through interaction - communication between teacher and student helps internalize linguistic norms. Thus, grammar and syntax instruction should not isolate learners but engage them in collaborative learning: discussions, pair work, and peer feedback sessions.

Grammar and syntax are the essential frameworks through which language operates. Their effective teaching requires more than memorizing rules - it demands meaningful, contextual, and communicative engagement.

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TASK-BASED ASSESSMENT: MEASURING PERFORMANCE THROUGH MEANINGFUL TASKS

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Abstract: Task-Based Assessment (TBA) is an emerging and influential approach within English language teaching, especially for young learners in primary education. Unlike traditional assessments that emphasize discrete language forms, TBA evaluates how effectively learners use language in authentic, goal-oriented tasks. This paper explores the theoretical basis of TBA, outlines its benefits and challenges, and provides detailed examples of how teachers can design and implement task-based assessments in primary English classrooms. By prioritizing communicative competence and learner engagement, TBA offers educators a framework that aligns teaching, learning, and assessment in meaningful ways. Practical strategies for integrating formative and summative assessment, rubric design, and technology-supported assessment are discussed. Implications for teacher development and curriculum reform are also highlighted.

Keywords: Task-Based Assessment, Communicative Competence, Young Learners, Primary Education, Performance-Based Assessment, Formative Assessment, Summative Assessment, Rubrics, Authentic Tasks

Introduction: In language education, assessment is not merely a means of measuring learning outcomes; it also influences how teachers teach and how students learn. In many primary classrooms, language assessment remains dominated by traditional paper-based tests that measure grammar, vocabulary, and spelling in isolation. However, such tests do not fully capture learners' ability to use English for real communication. Task-Based Assessment

(TBA), rooted in Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), seeks to address this gap by evaluating learners' performance on tasks that simulate authentic language use. For young learners, who learn best through meaningful interaction and play, TBA offers opportunities for holistic assessment that reflects both linguistic and cognitive development.

Literature review: The theoretical foundation of Task-Based Assessment lies in communicative competence theory (Hymes, 1972) and constructivist learning principles, which view knowledge as actively constructed through experience. TBLT, developed by researchers such as Prabhu (1987), Ellis (2003), and Nunan (2004), advocates using communicative tasks as the central unit of teaching and assessment. Within this framework, tasks are defined as activities that require learners to use language meaningfully to achieve a goal, such as describing a picture, planning a trip, or solving a problem.

According to Ellis (2003), a task involves a primary focus on meaning, the use of real-world processes of language use, and an outcome that can be evaluated. Assessment within a task-based framework thus focuses on performance outcomes rather than linguistic accuracy alone. Willis and Willis (2007) argue that meaningful communication provides the best context for evaluating language proficiency because it reflects how language is used outside the classroom. Carless (2012) and Butler (2018) extend this argument to young learners, emphasizing that age-appropriate tasks promote motivation, collaboration, and creativity—key aspects of language development in early education.

Discussion and analysis: Implementing Task-Based Assessment with primary learners requires balancing authenticity with developmental appropriateness. Teachers must design tasks that are engaging, achievable, and relevant to children's real-life experiences. For instance, tasks such as 'planning a birthday party,' 'designing a dream classroom,' or 'acting out a market scene' encourage learners to use English to express ideas, negotiate meaning, and collaborate with peers. Each of these activities offers a natural context for assessing multiple language skills simultaneously—listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Assessment in a task-based context can take several forms. Formative assessment includes ongoing teacher observations, peer and self-assessment, and reflective discussions. For example, during a 'shopping role play,' the teacher might observe how students initiate requests, respond politely, and use vocabulary related to food or money. Feedback can be provided immediately, emphasizing communication success rather than grammatical perfection. Such continuous, low-stakes assessment reduces anxiety and supports language development through constructive feedback.

Summative assessment in TBA can involve performance-based projects or presentations. For example, students might create a poster titled 'My Favorite Animal,' prepare short speeches, or record digital storytelling projects. The assessment criteria can be organized in rubrics that evaluate task completion, clarity, interaction, vocabulary range, and fluency. Butler (2018) suggests using age-appropriate rubrics with simple descriptors, such as 'uses words clearly,' 'works well with classmates,' or 'shares ideas in English.' This helps young learners understand how they are being assessed and encourages them to take ownership of their learning.

Another key advantage of TBA is its ability to integrate assessment with instruction. When teachers use tasks as both learning and assessment tools, they can observe how students progress naturally over time. For example, a 'group story creation' task may reveal development in sentence structure, vocabulary, and narrative skills as learners collaborate. Teachers can use observation checklists focusing on aspects like turn-taking, pronunciation, and expression. Over several weeks, repeated exposure to similar communicative tasks allows teachers to document progress more reliably than traditional tests.

Challenges remain in implementing TBA effectively. Teachers often struggle with time constraints, classroom management, and assessment reliability. Scoring subjective performances can be complex, particularly in large classes. However, research suggests that well-designed rubrics, peer assessment, and teacher moderation meetings can increase consistency and fairness (Carless, 2012). Professional development workshops that train teachers in task design, feedback strategies, and rubric use are essential to ensure success. Additionally, involving learners in co-creating assessment criteria can enhance transparency and motivation.

Pedagogical implications: For effective implementation of TBA in primary English classrooms, several pedagogical implications emerge. First, teachers should design tasks that reflect real-life communication and encourage collaboration. Tasks must align with learners' cognitive and emotional development levels. Second, assessment rubrics should balance linguistic accuracy and communicative effectiveness. Third, classroom environments should support creativity and experimentation, where mistakes are seen as part of the learning process. Finally, continuous professional support and curriculum alignment are vital to ensure that assessment practices remain consistent and educationally meaningful.

Task-Based Assessment represents a significant shift from testing knowledge to evaluating performance. For young learners, it transforms assessment into an engaging and developmental process that values communication and collaboration. By integrating assessment within authentic classroom activities, teachers can better capture learners' true abilities and growth. Although challenges such as time management and standardization exist, the pedagogical benefits of TBA-enhanced motivation, authenticity, and formative feedback make it an essential component of modern primary English education. Continued research and teacher training will be crucial to fully realize its potential in diverse educational contexts.

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TEACHING LANGUAGES TO YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH SONGS AND STORIES

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Abstract: Language teaching to young learners has always been an area of interest for educators and researchers who seek to identify the most effective and age-appropriate instructional methods. Young learners, usually defined as children aged between four and ten, possess unique cognitive, emotional, and linguistic characteristics that require creative and engaging pedagogical techniques. Traditional grammar-focused methods often fail to capture their attention or stimulate meaningful learning. Therefore, educators increasingly emphasize the use of songs and stories as tools for language instruction. These two methods offer an enjoyable and natural way of acquiring linguistic knowledge through exposure, repetition,

and meaningful context. This article discusses two major aspects: the role of songs and the role of stories in teaching languages to young learners, illustrating how each contributes to vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation development, and motivation.

Keywords: young learners, songs, TPR, effective storytelling, illustrating, linguistic, knowledge.

The role of songs in language learning: Songs have long been considered one of the most powerful tools for language teaching because they combine linguistic input with music, rhythm, and movement. According to Coyle and Gómez Gracia (2014), songs help young learners retain new words and expressions through repetition and melody. Unlike traditional drills, songs introduce vocabulary and grammar patterns in a memorable and emotionally engaging way. The repetitive structure of songs enhances both short-term and long-term memory retention, allowing children to internalize linguistic forms without conscious effort.

Moreover, songs are effective in developing pronunciation and listening comprehension. The rhythm and intonation patterns in songs mirror natural speech, helping learners grasp the prosody and stress patterns of the target language. For example, teaching children the song 'Head, Shoulders, Knees, and Toes' not only introduces vocabulary related to body parts but also helps them internalize rhythm and syllable stress. The act of singing along improves fluency, as children subconsciously mimic native-like pronunciation.

Songs also play an essential role in reducing anxiety and increasing motivation in the classroom. As Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982) suggests, learners acquire language more efficiently when they are relaxed and motivated. Singing provides a joyful, low-pressure environment that encourages participation. Even shy or less confident learners tend to join in group singing activities, which enhances their sense of belonging and linguistic confidence. Furthermore, songs expose children to cultural elements of the target language. For instance, traditional English songs such as "Old MacDonald Had a Farm" or "London Bridge is Falling Down" offer insights into Western culture and customs, thereby broadening students' intercultural awareness.

In practical classroom settings, teachers can use songs in various ways. One effective method is the 'Listen and Do' approach, where learners perform actions related to the lyrics—similar to Total Physical Response (TPR). For example, when singing 'If You're Happy and You Know It,' students clap, stomp, or nod according to the words, reinforcing meaning through physical movement. Another strategy involves fill-in-the-blank lyric exercises, where teachers remove key words and ask students to listen carefully and complete them. This improves both listening accuracy and vocabulary recall. Teachers can also integrate songs into thematic lessons; for instance, a song about weather can accompany a unit on seasons and clothing, creating strong conceptual connections.

Teaching young learners a foreign language requires creative and engaging methods that suit their developmental stage. Among the most effective techniques are songs and stories, which combine entertainment with language input. Both methods are based on the idea that learning is more effective when it is enjoyable and meaningful (Cameron, 2001).

Stories are equally significant in the language classroom, serving as a bridge between linguistic learning and cognitive development. Storytelling allows learners to encounter vocabulary and grammatical structures in meaningful, contextualized situations. According to Albaladejo, Coyle, and Roca de Larios (2018), preschool learners exposed to stories demonstrated higher levels of vocabulary recognition compared to those who learned words through isolated drills. This indicates that stories enable children to link words to events, emotions, and characters, which aids in deeper understanding and retention.

From a cognitive perspective, stories stimulate imagination and critical thinking. As children follow a narrative, they learn to predict events, infer meanings, and understand cause-and-effect relationships-all of which are crucial cognitive skills. Linguistically, storytelling introduces discourse markers, connectors, and complex sentence structures naturally. For instance, while reading 'Goldilocks and the Three Bears,' children are exposed to sequencing words such as 'first,' 'then,' and 'finally,' as well as adjectives describing size, quantity, and emotion.

In conclusion, both songs and stories are indispensable tools for teaching languages to young learners. They transform language learning from a mechanical process into a meaningful, enjoyable, and emotionally rich experience. Songs enhance memory, pronunciation, and motivation through rhythm and melody, while stories foster comprehension, imagination, and emotional engagement. Together, they form a balanced approach that supports not only linguistic development but also cultural and cognitive growth. As research shows, students exposed to songs and stories achieve greater vocabulary retention and demonstrate more positive attitudes toward language learning.

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SA'DULLA HAKIMNING “OLIS YULDUZ” DOSTONI HAQIDA MULOHAZALAR

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Annotatsiya: “Olis Yulduz” dostoni, insonning ichki dunyosidagi intilishlar va umidlar haqida hikoya qiladi. Doston insonning o'z maqsadlari sari intilishi, shu bilan birga, hayotning qiyinchiliklari va sinovlari bilan kurashish jarayonini tasvirlaydi. Falsafiy jihatdan bu asar, insonning o'z orzulariga erishish yo'lidagi sabr-toqati va matonatini ulug'laydi. Tarbiyaviy ahamiyati esa, o'quvchilarga maqsad sari intilish, orzularni ta'qib etish va hayot sinovlariga bardoshli bo'lish kabi qadriyatlarni singdiradi. Shuningdek, asar insonlarga o'z qobiliyatlariga ishonch hosil qilish va ularni rivojlantirishga undaydi. Ushbu maqolamiz shu haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Doston, obraz, bosh qahramon, poetika, ramziy-falsafiy asar, tip, dunyoqarash, to'qima obraz, tarixiy shaxs.

Abstract: The epic “*Olis Yulduz*” tells the story of human aspirations and hopes within one's inner world. It depicts a person's pursuit of their goals and the struggle with life's difficulties and trials. Philosophically, the work glorifies human patience and perseverance on the path toward achieving dreams. Its educational value lies in instilling in readers such qualities as striving for goals, pursuing dreams, and enduring life's challenges. Furthermore,

the work encourages individuals to believe in their own abilities and to develop them. This article discusses these aspects in detail.

Keywords: Epic, image, main character, poetics, symbolic-philosophical work, type, worldview, fictional image, historical figure.

Adabiyot insoniyat tafakkurining eng yuksak mahsuli bo'lib, uning eng nozik his-tuyg'ularini, orzu-umidlarini, ezgulik sari intilishlarini aks ettiradi. Shu boisdan, adabiy asarlar inson ruhiyatiga bevosita ta'sir etuvchi, uning dunyoqarashini shakllantiruvchi kuchli vosita sifatida qadrlanadi. Bu jihatdan "Olis yulduz" dostoni o'zining chuqur falsafiy mazmuni, tarixiy asoslari, ramziy obrazlari va badiiy go'zalligi bilan adabiyotimizning eng yuksak namunalari qatoridan munosib o'rin egallaydi. Ushbu doston nafaqat badiiy asar sifatida, balki inson ma'naviyati va ruhiy olamini yorituvchi falsafiy mushohada sifatida ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Dostonning o'qi – inson, uning orzu-intilishlari, ichki kurashlari va ma'naviy izlanishlaridir. "Olis yulduz" dostonida bu jihatlar chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Bosh qahramon Sparangiz obrazi orqali muallif insonning ruhi, orzusi va tafakkurining eng chuqur qatlamlariga kirib boradi. Sparangiz – shunchaki obraz emas, u o'zida butun bir ma'naviy maktabni mujassam etgan timsoldir. Uning harakati, qarorlari va kurashi orqali biz inson qalbidagi ezgulik, mardlik va fidoyilik singari yuksak fazilatlarining yorqin aksini ko'ramiz.[1,74 b]

Tabiat faqat tashqi dunyo sifatida emas, balki insonning ruhiy kechinmalarini aks ettiruvchi bir o'lkaga aylangan. Doston davomida, Sparangiz va boshqa qahramonlar tabiatda o'zlarini yakkalanib, qo'rqib, hayajonlanib yoki baxtli his qilishadi. Misol uchun, dostonning ayrim joylarida o'tgan daryolar, tepalar va boshqa tabiiy manzaralar insonning ichki ruhiy holatiga va uning jamiyatdagi o'rniga ta'sir qiladigan omil sifatida ishlatiladi. Ushbu tabiatning kuchli tasviri orqali, insonning his-tuyg'ulari, baxt va umid izlanishlari, shuningdek, kurashlar va shafqatsizliklar aniq ko'rsatiladi.[2,304 b]

Tabiat bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lgan boshqa muhim jihat esa insonning tabiatni anglash va undan to'g'ri foydalanish masalasidir. "Olis yulduz" dostonida tabiat va inson o'rtasidagi bu bog'liqlikda har bir qahramon o'zining tabiiy muhitida, tabiatning qonunlariga rioya qilgan holda hayot kechiradi. Tabiat insonni tarbiyalaydi, unga kuch va iroda beradi, lekin inson ham tabiatni hurmat qilib, uning qonunlariga amal qilishi lozim.[3,119 b] Dostonning markazida joylashgan Mitra timsoli bu g'oyani ta'kidlaydi: Mitra, tabiatni, yer va osmonni boshqaruvchi kuch sifatida, insonlarga to'g'ri yo'l ko'rsatadi va ularni zulmatdan nurlikka olib chiqadi. Bu tabiiy qonunlarga bo'ysunish, shuningdek, insonning o'zaro munosabatlarini ham ijobiy yo'lda rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Tabiatning inson uchun muhim rol o'ynashi dostonning bir nechta voqealarida yoritilgan. Masalan, Sparangizning tabiiy muhitga bo'lgan munosabati, uning yurtini va xalqini sevishi, o'z hayotini va maqsadlarini tabiat bilan bog'lab tushunishi uning ruhiy kuchini oshiradi. Tabiatga qarshi chiqish yoki uni e'tiborsiz qoldirish, insonning yomonlikka va yovuzlikka qarshi kurashdagi zaifligini ko'rsatadi.[4,303b] Shunday qilib, tabiat bilan insonning munosabati faqat tashqi voqelik sifatida qolmay, balki ichki dunyoning shakllanishida va insonning ma'naviy o'sishida muhim omil bo'ladi.

Dostonning yakunida, Sparangiz va boshqa qahramonlarning tabiat bilan aloqasi orqali insoniyatning abadiy umidi va maqsadiga erishishi tasvirlanadi. Tabiat faqat tashqi dunyo emas, balki insonning ichki borligining bir qismi sifatida, uning baxtli yoki baxtsiz hayotini belgilovchi kuchdir. Bu bog'liqlik, inson va tabiatning o'zaro muvozanatda bo'lishi kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. Asar orqali o'quvchi tabiat va inson o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqani anglab, hayotning ma'nosini chuqurroq tushunadi.

“Olis yulduz” dostoni, insoniy hayotning eng asosiy tamoyillaridan biri – yaxshilik va yomonlikning abadiy kurashi haqida hikoya qiladi. Ushbu doston o‘zining chuqur ma’no-mazmuni va o‘tkir badiiy tasvirlari orqali o‘quvchini insoniy mohiyatning eng muhim savollarini o‘ylashga undaydi. Doston voqealarida yaxshilik va yomonlikning o‘zaro to‘qnashuvi nafaqat tarixiy voqealar, balki inson qalbi va jamiyatdagi muammolar timsolida [5,3 b] ham namoyon bo‘ladi.

Doston bosh qahramoni Sparangizning hayoti va taqdiri yaxshilik va yomonlikning ziddiyatli kurashi asosida rivojlanadi. U o‘z xalqiga bo‘lgan sadoqati, erkinlik uchun kurashi va insoniy fazilatlari bilan namoyon bo‘lsa, yomonlik esa nafaqat dushmanlar timsolida, balki ba‘zan ichki ruhiy kurash shaklida ham o‘zini ko‘rsatadi. Bu holat insonning o‘zini anglash jarayonidagi ziddiyatlarni ochib beradi.

Dostonda yaxshilikning ramzi sifatida Mitra – tinchlik va hayotbaxshlik timsoli ko‘rsatilgan. Mitra insonlarni mashaqqatlardan olib chiqishga, yaxshilik va muhabbatni yoyishga da’vat etadi. Ushbu falsafiy g‘oya Sparangizning harakatlarida ham aks etadi. Sparangiz jang maydonida ham, o‘z shaxsiy hayotida ham adolat, halollik va insoniylik tamoyillariga amal qiladi. U yurtiga va o‘z xalqiga bo‘lgan sadoqati tufayli shaxsiy manfaatlarini qurbon qilishga tayyor.

Sparangizning harakatlari, ayniqsa, yurtini himoya qilish yo‘lida qilgan fidokorliklari dostonning yaxshilikni ulug‘lovchi markaziy fikrlaridan biridir. Uning qalbidagi vatanparvarlik, mehr-muhabbat va adolat hissi yaxshilikning inson qalbidagi qudratini ko‘rsatadi. Bunday fazilatlar orqali Sparangiz o‘zining kuchli ichki qahramonligini namoyish etadi.

Ushbu obraz adolat va halollik uchun kurashuvchi, xalqining ozodligi va baxt-saodati uchun o‘zini qurbon qilishga tayyor bo‘lgan inson timsolidir. Sparangizning xatti-harakatlari va qarorlari uning insoniy fazilatlarini ochib beradi, ayni paytda bu fazilatlar o‘quvchiga ibrat bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Sparangizning har bir harakati uning insoniy fazilatlarini yuksak darajada ko‘rsatadi. U yurtining mustaqilligi va tinchligini himoya qilish yo‘lida fidokorlik qiladi. Dostondagi ko‘plab voqealar shuni tasdiqlaydiki, Sparangiz uchun vatanparvarlik va sadoqat shaxsiy manfaatlardan ustun turadi. Uning harakatlari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, haqiqiy qahramonlik nafaqat jang maydonida, balki ichki kurashlarda ham namoyon bo‘ladi.[6,12 b]

Sparangiz obrazi nafaqat tashqi dushmanlarga qarshi kurashda, balki ichki ruhiy kurashlarda ham namoyon bo‘ladi. Uning o‘z-o‘zi bilan olib borgan ichki kurashlari – bu insonning shaxsiy izlanishlari va ma’naviy o‘sishining yorqin misoli. Dostondagi ba’zi voqealar uning shubhalari va qo‘rquvlari haqida so‘zlasa-da, oxir-oqibat u maqsadidan chekinmaslikni tanlaydi.

Sparangiz obrazi o‘quvchi uchun haqiqiy ibrat namunasi bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Uning qahramonligi, fidoyiligi va adolatparvarligi hayotdagi ko‘plab muammolarni qanday hal qilish mumkinligi haqida o‘ylashga undaydi. Unga taqlid qilish orqali insonlar o‘z ma’naviyatini yuksaltirishi va jamiyatga foydali bo‘lishi mumkin.

Sparangiz obrazi “Olis yulduz” dostoni markazida turuvchi va uning ma’nosini ochib beruvchi asosiy qahramonlardan biridir. Uning vatanparvarligi, jasorati va insoniyligi o‘quvchi qalbida chuqur iz qoldiradi. Ushbu obraz adolat, sadoqat va tinchlik uchun kurashning abadiy qadriyat ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Sa’dulla Hakimning dostonlarining kompozitsiyasi, an’anaviy O‘zbek adabiyotidan ilhomlanib, zamonaviy mavzular bilan uyg‘unlashgan holda yaratiladi. Shoirning har bir asari o‘ziga xos tuzilishga ega bo‘lib, u muayyan bir qahramon yoki bir guruh qahramonlarning ichki dunyosi va tashqi voqealarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Hakimning

dostonlari, voqea va lavhalar orqali insoniy tuyg'ularni, jamiyatdagi muammolarni va tabiat bilan munosabatlarni o'ziga xos tarzda ifodalaydi. Bu dostonlar, odatda, bir nechta qismlarga bo'linadi, har bir qism o'z ichiga muayyan mazmun va rivojlanishni oladi. Shu tariqa muallif o'quvchilarni chuqurroq fikrlashga va mavzuni kengroq tushunishga jalb etadi.

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA INGLIZ TILI DARSLARINI BOSQICHMA-BOSQICH VA SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili darslarini boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun qanday qilib bosqichma-bosqich ,ketma-ket va samarali tarzda tashkil etish haqida yoritilgan. Shu bilan birgalikda ushbu darslarda o'quvchining faolligi va chet tillarini boshlang'ich sinflarda qanday qilib to'g'ri shakllantirish haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz, til, boshlang'ich, sinf, bosqichma – bosqich, zamonaviy, metodlar, o'qitish.

Annotation: This article is illuminated by the organization of English language lessons how to organize the primary position, in a row and effectively. At the same time, these classes are illuminated on the activity of the student and how to properly formulate foreign languages in primary schools.

Keywords: English, language, primary, grade, step-by-step, modern, methods, teaching.

Boshlang'ich ta'limda ingliz tili o'qitishning zamonaviy maqsad, mazmun va texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish, kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarga ingliz tili o'qitish amaliyotida to'plangan an'anaviy va xorijiy tajribalarni umumlashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi o'quv qo'llanmalarining yetishmasligi oqibatida mazkur soha uchun pedagog kadrlar tayyorlash jarayonida yetarlicha samaradorlikka erishilmayapti.

Bugungi kunda dunyo aholisining qariyb 60 foizi ikki yoki undan ortiq tillarda so'zlasha olishi barchaga ma'lum. Jahonda globallashtirish jarayonlarini tezlashtirish, erkin bozor munosabatlariga o'tish va ishlab chiqarishga yuqori texnologiyalarni joriy etishning rag'batlantirilishi «lingvistik kapital»ga, ya'ni chet tillarni (ayniqsa, ingliz tilini) mukammal egallagan mutaxassislariga ehtiyojni kuchaytirmoqda. Chet til ta'limida sifat va samaradorlikni ta'minlash maqsadida chet tillarni o'rganish/o'rgatish yoshini qisqartirish tajribasi ommalashib bormoqda. Bunga «the younger the better / early is better» mazmunidagi tushunchaning keng tarqalganligi sabab bo'ldi.

Boshlang'ich sinflarda, ayniqsa, birinchi sinfda o'quvchilarga chet tillarni o'rgatishda o'quvchining yoshi, fiziologik, psixologik xususiyatlarini hisobga olish kerak. Qarorda ta'kidlanganidek, birinchi sinflarda o'yin tarzidagi darslar va og'zaki nutq darslari shaklida chet tillarini o'rgatishni amalga oshirish, haqiqatan, kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarga mosligidir. Ta'limda o'yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, eng samarali vositalardan biridir. O'yin davomida ularning tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi, fikrlashi kengayib boradi. Olimlar ta'limga o'yin orqali yondashuv ta'lim jarayonida osonlashtiradi, deb hisoblagan. Nafaqat osonlashtiradi, balki bu fanga qiziqishini kuchaytirib, bolani chuqur bilim olishiga undaydi. Shubhasiz, mamlakatimiz ta'lim dargohlarida xorijiy tillar xonalarini zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari o'qitishning ilg'or texnik vositalari bilan jihozlash, teleradiokanallarda bolalar va o'smirlarni xorijiy tillarga o'rgatuvchi ko'rsatuv va eshittirishlarni berib borish, boshqa mamlakatlar tarixi va madaniyati, jahon ilm-fani va texnik yangiliklariga bag'ishlangan ilmiy-ommabop xorijiy badiiy va multiplikatsion filmlarni o'zbekcha subtitr yordamida muntazam namoyish etish yoshlarimizga dunyo xalqlarining o'tmishi, madaniyati, ilm-fani bilan yaqindan tanishishi imkonini berdi.

Til bilish ko'plab keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Dunyo kezishga, biznesga, ilm olishga, dunyoqarashiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, albatta. Chet tillari maktab o'quvchilariga ya'ni, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga bosqichma – bosqich o'rgatilishi yo'lga qo'yilgan. Bu jarayonda 1-sinf o'quvchilariga o'zlariga mos tarzda, asosan, multimedial va og'zaki o'rgatish metodlaridan foydalanish yaxshi samara beradi. 1-sinf o'quvchilarida o'zlarining ona tilisi haqida to'lliq 84 tushuncha va bilim hosil qilmasdan turib ularga ingliz tili alifbosi va yozuv malakasini mutlaqo noto'g'ri hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun ham ingliz tilidan ularga ilk saboqlar o'yinlar, multimedia vositalari va og'zaki usulda o'rgatiladi, so'ngra o'quvchilar 2-sinfga o'tishgach ularda savod o'rgatish davri to'lliq yakunlangan bo'ladi va shu davrdan boshlab ularga ingliz alifbosi va yozuv malakalarini o'rnatish va o'quvchilar bilimni shakllantirishni yo'lga qo'yish darkor. Shu tariqa ularda chet tilini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish amalga oshirish mumkin. Ingliz tili o'zining ko'plab jihatlari va qiziqarli xususiyatlari bilan o'quvchining qiziqishiga va bu tilni jiddiy o'rganishga olib keladi.

Ingliz tilini o'qitishda o'quvchilarni yosh va psixologik xususiyatlarini inobatga olgan holda, ulardagi chet tilini o'zlashtirishga bo'lgan qiziqish, ehtiyojni to'la qondirishga yordam beruvchi pedagogik texnologiyalarga asoslangan zamonaviy didaktik ishlanmalarni tayyorlash va ularni amalga oshirishning mustahkam mexanizmini ishlab chiqish muammoning amaliy yechimini ta'minlaydi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga til o'rganishni majburiyat sifatida emas, balki qiziqarli o'yinlar va metodlardan foydalangan holda olib borishi, ularning kelajakda oladigan bilimlari uchun poydevor bo'lib xizmat qilishi

mumkin. Shunday ekan, ta'lim tizimida ham o'z oldiga erkin fikrlovchi, barkamol, yetuk shaxsni tarbiyalashni vazifa qilib qo'yar ekan, kelgusida biz bo'lajak o'qituvchilar innovatsion texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish yo'llarini yanada mukammal ishlab chiqish bilan o'z hissamizni qo'shishimiz mumkin.

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida chet tillarini o'qitishning ahamiyati, o'quvchilarda til kompetensiyasini shakllantirish, chet tili o'qitish jarayonida qo'llaniladigan zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va kommunikativ yondashuvning roli yoritilgan. Shuningdek, kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning psixologik xususiyatlari hamda o'qituvchining kasbiy mahorati ta'lim sifatiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, chet tili, o'qitish metodikasi, kommunikativ yondashuv, kompetensiya, motivatsiya, innovatsiya.

Kirish: Bugungi globallashuv jarayonida har bir insonning muvaffaqiyati ko'p jihatdan uning xorijiy tillarni bilish darajasiga bog'liq. Xalqaro hamkorlikning kengayishi, raqamli texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi va dunyo bo'ylab axborot almashuvining tezlashuvi chet tillarini o'rganishni hayotiy zaruratga aylantirdi. Shu sababli, O'zbekiston Respublikasida ham so'nggi yillarda chet tillarini, ayniqsa ingliz tilini o'qitish tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha keng qamrovli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Boshlang'ich ta'lim bu jarayonning eng muhim bo'g'inidir. Chunki aynan shu davrda bolaning bilishga bo'lgan qiziqishi, eshitish, eslab qolish va talaffuzni takrorlash qobiliyatlari faol rivojlanadi. Shu boisdan chet tili o'qitishni aynan boshlang'ich bosqichdan yo'lga qo'yish o'quvchining kelajakdagi til o'rganish salohiyatiga poydevor yaratadi. Kichik yoshdagi bolalar chet tilini o'zlashtirishda tabiiy usullarni - o'yin, qo'shiq, tasvir, harakat orqali o'rganishni afzal ko'radi. Shu sababli, dars jarayonida o'qituvchi grammatikani murakkab tarzda emas, balki sodda, hayotiy misollar va ko'rgazmali vositalar orqali tushuntirishi lozim. Bolaning diqqatini uzoq vaqt bir joyda ushlab turish qiyin bo'lgani uchun, darsda faol metodlar - o'yinli topshiriqlar, rolli sahnalar, rasmlar asosida so'zlashish kabi usullar katta samara beradi. Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tilini o'qitishning maqsadi grammatikani chuqur o'rgatish emas, balki o'quvchilarda muloqotga kirishish, so'zlarni

tushunish va fikrini ifodalashga bo'lgan ishonchni shakllantirishdir. Shu jihatdan kommunikativ yondashuv alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu metod o'quvchini faol subyekt sifatida darsga jalb qiladi: u dars jarayonida tinglovchi emas, balki so'zlovchi, fikr bildiruvchi va muloqot ishtirokchisiga aylanadi.

Chet tili o'qitishda texnologiyalarni qo'llash ham zamon talabi hisoblanadi. Multimediali vositalar, interaktiv ta'lim platformalari, audio va video materiallardan foydalanish darsni jonlantiradi, o'quvchilarda mustaqil o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishni kuchaytiradi. Misol uchun, qisqa multfilmlar, qo'shiqlar, audio so'z mashqlari orqali o'quvchilar so'z boyligini kengaytiradi va talaffuzni to'g'rilaydi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari bilan ishlashda o'qituvchi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki ruhiy qo'llab-quvvatlovchi rolni ham bajaradi. Kichik yutuqlar uchun berilgan maqtov, tabassum yoki rag'bat bolada o'rganishga bo'lgan ishtiyoqni yanada oshiradi. Aksincha, darsda qat'iy yoki sovuq muomala o'quvchining ishonchini pasaytirishi mumkin. Shu sababli, o'qituvchi har bir o'quvchining yosh va psixologik xususiyatlarini inobatga olib, darsni ijobiy muhitda tashkil etishi kerak.

Chet tili o'qitishning yana bir muhim jihati - bu madaniyatlararo muloqotni shakllantirishdir. Har bir til - o'sha xalqning madaniyati, urf-odatlar va tafakkuri bilan bog'liq. Shu bois, chet tili darslarida o'quvchilarga nafaqat so'z va grammatik qoidalar, balki o'sha xalqning madaniyati, bayramlari, qadriyatlar haqida qisqa ma'lumot berish foydali. Bu esa o'quvchilarda bag'rikenglik, hurmat va dunyoqarashning kengayishiga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy ta'limda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv muhim o'rin tutadi. Ya'ni, o'quvchi nafaqat bilim olishi, balki uni amalda qo'llay olishi kerak. Chet tili darslarida bu yondashuv "so'zlay olish", "tinglab tushunish", "yozish" va "o'qish" kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish orqali amalga oshiriladi. Masalan, kichik suhbatlar tashkil etish, so'z zanjiri o'yinlari yoki qisqa matn yozish mashqlari orqali o'quvchi o'z bilimini hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo'llashni o'rganadi. Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tili o'qitishda muammolar ham mavjud. Ba'zi hollarda o'qituvchilarning malakasi yetarli emas, o'quv resurslari va texnik jihozlar kam. Bularni bartaraf etish uchun doimiy malaka oshirish kurslari, yangi darsliklar yaratish, xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ayniqsa, o'qituvchilarning talaffuz, nutq o'stirish va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni dars jarayoniga integratsiya qilish bo'yicha ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish zarur.

Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tili o'rganishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati ham katta. Chet tilini o'rganayotgan bola yangi madaniyat bilan tanishadi, dunyoqarashi kengayadi, mustaqil fikrlash va o'z fikrini ifoda etish ko'nikmasi rivojlanadi. Bu esa keyinchalik uning o'qishdagi muvaffaqiyatlariga, shaxsiy rivojlanishiga va jamiyatdagi faol ishtirokiga zamin yaratadi. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida so'nggi yillarda chet tili o'qitishni 1-sinfdan boshlash to'g'risidagi qaror ham shu maqsadga xizmat qiladi. Bu orqali davlat yosh avlodni erta bosqichdanoq global dunyoda erkin muloqot qila oladigan, bilimli va raqobatbardosh shaxs sifatida tarbiyalashni ko'zlagan.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tillarining o'rnini nihoyatda muhim va dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Chunki aynan boshlang'ich sinflarda bola shaxs sifatida shakllana boshlaydi, uning dunyoqarashi, fikrlash doirasi, nutq madaniyati, eshitish va o'rganish qobiliyatlari faol rivojlanadi. Shu davrda chet tilini o'rganish orqali o'quvchilar yangi tovush tizimlarini farqlash, eslab qolish, so'z birikmalarini to'g'ri talaffuz qilish va eng muhimi - o'z fikrini begona tilda ifoda etish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'ladi. Bu esa ularning kelajakdagi ta'lim bosqichlarida chet tilini mukammal o'zlashtirishiga mustahkam poydevor yaratadi. Chet tilini erta o'rgatish bolaning kognitiv (aql-idrok) rivojlanishiga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, bir necha tilni erta yoshda o'rgangan bolalarda tafakkur

moslashuvchanligi, eslab qolish qobiliyati va ijodiy fikrlash darajasi yuqori bo'ladi. Shuningdek, bunday o'quvchilar boshqa fanlarni o'zlashtirishda ham faolroq bo'ladi, chunki ular turli madaniyatlar, so'z boyluklari va ifoda shakllarini solishtirishni o'rganadi. Bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimida chet tillarini 1-sinfidan o'qitish qarorining amaliy natijalari sezilmoqda. O'quvchilarning so'z boyligi kengaymoqda, ularning muloqot qilish istagi oshmoqda va eng muhimi - chet tili o'rganishga ijobiy munosabat shakllanmoqda. Biroq bu jarayonni yanada samarali qilish uchun o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, zamonaviy o'quv-uslubiy majmualarni yaratish, texnologik vositalarni keng joriy etish zarur.

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EKOLOGIYANI ASRASHNING AHAMIYATI VA UNDA TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola orqali ekologik muvozanatni saqlash va tabiatni asrashda texnologiyalarning o'rni hamda ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Unda sun'iy intellekt, raqamli texnologiyalar, ekologik monitoring tizimlari, "yashil energiya" manbalari va ekologik ta'limning zamonaviy shakllari haqida so'z yuritiladi. Maqolada inson tafakkurining taraqqiyoti bilan texnologik yutuqlarning uyg'unlashuvi orqali tabiatni muhofaza qilish masalasiga yangicha yondashuv taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekologiya, texnologiya, sun'iy intellekt, yashil energiya, ekologik ta'lim, raqamli monitoring, tabiat muhofazasi.

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and significance of technologies in maintaining ecological balance and protecting nature. It discusses artificial intelligence, digital technologies, ecological monitoring systems, "green energy" sources, and modern forms of environmental education. The article proposes a new approach to environmental protection through the integration of technological achievements with the development of human thought.

Keywords: ecology, technology, artificial intelligence, green energy, environmental education, digital monitoring, nature conservation.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida insoniyat texnik taraqqiyotning cho'qqisiga chiqqan bo'lsa-da, tabiat bilan uyg'unlikni yo'qotmoqda. Atmosferaning isib borishi, suv va tuproqning ifloslanishi, chiqindilar miqdorining keskin ortishi kabi muammolar butun dunyo miqyosida ekologik xavf tug'dirmoqda. Shu bois ekologiyani asrash - zamonaviy jamiyatning eng dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir.

Texnologiyalar esa bu jarayonda faqat ishlab chiqarish vositasi emas, balki tabiatni asrash quroli sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Masalan, sun'iy intellekt tizimlari havoning sifatini tahlil qilish, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash jarayonini optimallashtirish, suv resurslarini kuzatish kabi vazifalarni bajaradi. Dronlar va IoT sensorlari yordamida o'rmon yong'inlari, suv toshqinlari va iqlim o'zgarishlarini oldindan ko'rish rivojlanmoqda. Zamonaviy ekologik siyosatda "raqamli tabiat" tushunchasi paydo bo'ldi - bu texnologiyalar orqali tabiatni kuzatish, tahlil qilish va muhofaza qilishning yangi bosqichidir. Masalan, sun'iy yo'ldoshlar yordamida o'rmonlarning holatini aniqlash, chiqindilar xaritasini tuzish yoki atmosfera tarkibini kuzatish mumkin. Shuningdek, blokcheyn texnologiyasi yordamida ekologik loyihalarning shaffofligini ta'minlash, har bir daraxt ekilishi yoki chiqindi qayta ishlanishini raqamli tarzda tasdiqlash mumkin. Bu esa insoniyat uchun ekologik mas'uliyatni oshiradi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, texnologiya va ekologiya uyg'unligi - bu faqat ilmiy g'oya emas, balki insoniyat kelajagi uchun yagona to'g'ri yo'ldir. Aristotel aytganidek, "tabiat hech narsani behuda yaratmaydi", shuning uchun texnologiya ham tabiatga xizmat qilgan holda, uning yaratuvchan kuchini qo'llab-quvvatlashi kerak. Shu tarzda texnologik yondashuvlarning afzalliklarini o'rganish - ekologik muammolarni hal etishda eng muhim bosqich hisoblanadi.

Texnologik yechimlarning ekologiyani muhofaza qilishdagi afzalliklari ko'p. Eng avvalo, ular aniqlik va tezkorlikni ta'minlaydi: sun'iy intellekt tizimlari ekologik o'zgarishlarni real vaqt rejimida tahlil qiladi. Raqamli monitoring tizimlari orqali havo, suv, tuproq sifati nazorat qilinadi, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash avtomatlashtiriladi. Shuningdek, texnologiyalar insoniyatga ekologik ongini shakllantirish imkonini beradi. Masalan, interaktiv platformalar, "EcoLearn" kabi onlayn dasturlar orqali yoshlarga ekologik madaniyat singdirilmoqda. Yashil energiya – kelajakning kafolati.

"Yashil energiya" - insoniyatning kelajakdagi barqaror hayot manbai. Quyosh, shamol, suv va biomassa energiyasi tabiiy muhitga zarar yetkazmasdan energiya ishlab chiqarish imkonini beradi. Bu yo'nalish texnologik taraqqiyotning ekologik yo'nalish bilan uyg'unlashgan eng yuksak shaklidir. O'zbekiston ham bu borada sezilarli yutuqlarga erishmoqda. "Yashil makon" umummilliy loyihasi, energiya tejamkor texnologiyalarni joriy etish, chiqindilarni qayta ishlovchi zavodlar qurilishi - bularning barchasi ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlash yo'lida amalga oshirilmoqda.

Ekologik ta'lim - bu insonda tabiatga nisbatan ongli munosabat, ekologik madaniyat va mas'uliyatni shakllantiruvchi jarayondir. U nafaqat nazariy bilim, balki amaliy faoliyatga asoslanadi. Bugungi kunda ekologik ta'lim faqat biologiya yoki geografiya darslarida emas, balki barcha ta'lim yo'nalishlarida muhim o'rin egallamoqda. Uning asosiy maqsadi - yosh avlodni tabiatni muhofaza qilish, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va ekologik muammolarni hal etishda faol ishtirok etishga tayyorlashdir. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar ekologik ta'limni yangi bosqichga olib chiqdi. Quyidagi texnologik yondashuvlar bu jarayonda eng samarali hisoblanadi:

a) Virtual laboratoriyalar va simulyatsiyalar

Virtual laboratoriyalar orqali o'quvchilar ekologik tajribalarni xavfsiz sharoitda o'tkazish imkoniyatiga ega. Masalan, ular ifloslanish manbalarining suv ekotizimiga ta'siri yoki atmosferadagi CO₂ darajasining o'zgarishini modellashtirishi mumkin. Bunday interaktiv tajribalar ekologik tushunchalarni chuqurroq anglashga yordam beradi.

b) Onlayn platformalar va mobil ilovalar "Google Earth", "EcoLearn", "iNaturalist" kabi ilovalar foydalanuvchilarga atrof-muhitni o'rganish, o'simlik va hayvon turlarini aniqlash hamda ekologik loyihalarda ishtirok etish imkonini beradi. Masalan, o'quvchilar smartfonlari yordamida mahalliy hududdagi o'simliklar haqida ma'lumot to'plab, ularni global ekologik

ma'lumotlar bazasiga joylashtirishadi. Bu orqali ular ilmiy hamjamiyat bilan hamkorlikda o'rganishadi.

c) Masofaviy ta'lim va media vositalari

Video darslar, ekologik hujjatli filmlar va interaktiv o'yinlar orqali ekologik muammolar yanada ta'sirchan tarzda yetkaziladi. Masalan, National Geographic Learning platformasi o'quvchilarni global ekologik jarayonlar haqida o'ylashga undovchi o'quv resurslarni taqdim etadi.

Ekologik muammolarni hal etishda inson ongi va bilim darajasi hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida interaktiv darslar, virtual laboratoriyalar, ekologik o'yinlar tashkil etilmoqda. Bu usullar yoshlarning tabiatga bo'lgan mehrini, mas'uliyatini oshiradi. Ekologik ta'lim nafaqat bilim berish, balki fikrlashni o'zgartirish jarayonidir. Agar inson raqamli tafakkurga ega bo'lsa, texnologiyalarni tabiatni himoya qilish vositasi sifatida ishlatadi. Texnologiya insoniyatning kuch-qudratini ifodalaydi, tabiat esa uning hayot manbai hisoblanadi. Agar bu ikki kuch o'rtasida muvozanat bo'lmasa, na taraqqiyot, na hayot bardavom bo'ladi. Shu bois, zamonaviy inson texnologiyani tabiatga qarshi emas, balki tabiat bilan hamkorlikda ishlaydigan tizim sifatida anglashni o'rganishi lozim. Sun'iy intellekt, raqamli tizimlar, "yashil energiya" va ekologik ta'lim uyg'unligi insoniyatni ongli taraqqiyot bosqichiga olib chiqadi. Bu - Aristotelning "tabiat - eng mukammal tartib" degan fikrining zamonaviy talqinidir. Shunday qilib, ekologiyani asrash va texnologiyani uyg'unlashtirish - bu faqat bugunning emas, balki insoniyat tarixining eng muhim vazifasidir.

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ZAMONAVIY YOSHLARNING KITONXONLIKDAN UZOQLASHISH SABABLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi davrda yoshlarning kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishining pasayib borishi sabablari va bu holatni yuzaga keltiruvchi omillar atroflicha tahlil qilingan. Maqolada shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va ommaviy madaniyatning yoshlar ongiga ta'siri, shuningdek, bu muammoni bartaraf etish yo'llari bo'yicha takliflar ham berilgan. Kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish va yoshlarni ma'naviy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari ham yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kitobxonlik, yoshlar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, raqamli texnologiyalar, ma'naviyat.

Kitob inson tafakkuri va ma'naviyatining asosi hisoblanadi. U insonni fikrlashga, tahlil qilishga, to'g'ri qaror qabul qilishga o'rgatadi. Qadimdan buyuk allomalarimiz kitob o'qishning ahamiyatini yuksak baholab, uni ilm va ma'rifat manbai sifatida ulug'lashgan. Hozirgi davrda esa, afsuski, yoshlar orasida kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqish sezilarli darajada kamayib bormoqda. Bunga turli omillar, jumladan, raqamli texnologiyalarning keng tarqalishi, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning jozibadorligi va ommaviy madaniyatning kuchayishi sabab bo'lmoqda. Mazkur maqolada ushbu jarayonning sabablari tahlil qilinadi hamda kitobxonlikni rivojlantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar keltiriladi.

Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar hayotimizning barcha jabhalariga chuqur kirib borgan. Smartfon, planshet, kompyuter va internet kabi vositalar yoshlar uchun asosiy axborot manbaiga aylangan. Ma'lumotlarni bir necha soniyada topish imkoniyati mavjud bo'lgani sababli, ular kitob o'qishga kamroq vaqt ajratmoqda. Natijada, o'qish madaniyati va tafakkur jarayoni sekin-asta sustlashmoqda. Kitob o'qish sabr-toqat, e'tibor va tahlilni talab qilsa-da, raqamli platformalarda ma'lumotlar tez va oson shaklda taqdim etiladi, bu esa yoshlarni chuqur o'ylash jarayonidan uzoqlashtiradi.

Instagram, Telegram, TikTok kabi ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlarning asosiy vaqtini egallab olgan. Ular foydalanuvchilarga ko'ngilochar kontent taqdim etadi, bu esa o'qishga bo'lgan e'tiborning pasayishiga olib keladi. Yoshlar o'z vaqtining katta qismini qisqa videolarni tomosha qilish yoki yozishmalarda o'tkazmoqda. Shu sababli, ular kitob o'qishga vaqt topolmaydi. Shu bilan birga, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda o'qish va bilim olish bilan bog'liq kontent ham mavjud bo'lsa-da, ularni iste'mol qilish madaniyati yetarli darajada shakllanmagan.

Bugungi kunda jamiyatda iste'molchilik qarashlari kuchayib borayotgani seziladi. Yoshlar orasida ko'proq moddiy qadriyatlar va tashqi ko'rinishga e'tibor kuchaygan. Bu holat ma'naviy boylik, bilim va tafakkurga e'tiborning kamayishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Ommaviy madaniyat mahsulotlari - seriallar, musiqalar va shoular yoshlarning bo'sh vaqtini egallab, o'qishga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytiradi.

Oilaviy va ta'limiy muhitning roli: Yoshlarning kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishining shakllanishida oilaning o'rni beqiyos. Afsuski, bugungi kunda ko'plab ota-onalar o'z farzandlariga kitob o'qish namunasini ko'rsata olmayapti. Ta'lim muassasalarida ham kitobxonlik madaniyatini targ'ib etish ishlari yetarlicha yo'lga qo'yilmagan. Maktab va oliy o'quv yurtlarida ko'proq imtihonlarga tayyorlov, test mashg'ulotlariga urg'u berilmoqda, badiiy asarlarni o'qish esa e'tibordan chetda qolmoqda.

Yoshlar o'rtasida kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishning kamayib borishi zamonaviy texnologiyalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va ommaviy madaniyat ta'sirining kuchayganidan dalolat beradi. Bu jarayon yoshlarning fikrlash, tahlil qilish va nutq madaniyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Shunday bo'lsa-da, bu muammoni bartaraf etish uchun oila, ta'lim muassasalari va jamiyat birgalikda harakat qilishi zarur. Maktablarda kitobxonlik haftaliklari, adabiy kechalar, o'qish marafonlari kabi tadbirlarni yo'lga qo'yish orqali yoshlarning kitobga bo'lgan muhabbatini qayta uyg'otish mumkin. Kitob insonning eng yaqin do'sti va hayot yo'lida yo'lboshchidir.

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TRANSLATION PROBLEMS IN COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY - SEMANTIC UNIVERSALS AND CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

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Annotation: This article explores the role of comparative typology in solving translation problems through focusing on how semantic universals, which exist worldwide in all languages, can help translators find common side between different linguistic systems. At the same time, this demonstrates how cultural differences create issues that universals are not able to solve. The study highlights examples where universal meanings are easily translated. The main idea of this demonstration that comparative typology not only studies compares languages but also provides useful tools for understanding translation difficulties in a world of linguistics.

Key words: comparative typology, typology, translation, semantic universals, cultural differences, linguistic equivalence, cross-linguistic analysis, intercultural communication, dynamic equivalence, formal equivalence.

As Bernard Comrie said: “Comparative typology is concerned with classifying languages according to their structural features and explaining the distribution of those features across the world’s language” [B. Comrie, 1981; 3]. Comparative typology studies similarities and differences between languages in order to reveal their universal features, so that it has always been one of the essential branches of the field of the linguistics. Translation, is a practical field where these theoretical findings are tested in real communication. While comparing and translating two languages, difficulties inevitably arise.

Initially, Joseph Greenberg’s ideas in the 1960s became a foundation for modern typology because J. Greenberg who is the first invented the idea of universals and discussed widely, researched on word order and implicational universals. His work showed that despite their diversity, languages share common structural principles. Later, Bernard Comrie continued this line of study by analyzing tense and paid attention to main systems’ aspect across languages, which is highly relevant to translation practice.

From the semantic perspective, being developed “Natural Semantic Metalanguage” theory, Anna Wierzbicka suggested there is a set of basic semantic universals common to all human languages through it. Her approach has been especially useful for translation field, after explaining how different cultures express universal human concepts.

In translation science, Eugene Nida played an important role by introducing the concepts of “formal equivalence” and “dynamic equivalence.” His theory highlighted that translation is not only about transforming meaning of the sentences from one language to another one using linguistic structure change but also about cultural meaning.

Mona Baker’s works on equivalence and corpus-based translation studies have shown how linguistic typology can be applied to real texts, revealing both universals and culture-specific difficulties.

Consequently, the overlap between comparative typology and translation highlights two aspects of the same issue: universality enables translation, while cultural differences pose challenges. This article seeks to examine how semantic universals assist translators and how cultural disparities continue to act as obstacles in cross-linguistic communication.

1. Semantic universals and their limits in translation: One of the biggest issues in translation is the balance between universality and particularity. Semantic universals, as discussed by Greenberg and Wierzbicka, suggest that all human languages share a core set of meanings such as mother and water concepts. These universals should, in theory, make translation easier

because they provide common ground. However, research shows that even these universals can vary in expression. Languages do not always segment the color spectrum in the same way [J. Lucy, 1997; 46]. For instance, the expression of “blue” does not exist in some languages as a certain and seen color term but is merged with green (as in Russian language it means - “синий” and “голубой”, but in some Turkish languages like Uzbek, “ko’k” can mean both “green” and “blue” – ko’m-ko’k maysalar). Translating such terms requires cultural and contextual sensitivity, not just dictionary equivalence.

2. *Cultural differences and untranslatable concepts*: Another major problem is the existence of culture-specific concepts that do not have direct equivalents in other languages. For instance, the Japanese word of *amae* (a kind of indulgent dependence in close relationships) has no exact equivalent in English or Uzbek. Similarly, Uzbek has culturally loaded terms like “mahalla” that are hard to translate into English or Russian, since the expression of “community” and “neighborhood” in Uzbek culture carries a set of social practices not found in Western vocabulary.

Typology helps us see why these gaps exist: languages encode reality based on cultural role. Translation scholars such as Eugene Nida and Mona Baker point out that equivalence have to be flexible — sometimes using formal equivalence (word-to-word) is impossible process, so dynamic equivalence (meaning-based) should be applied.

3. *Structural differences between languages and their effect on translation*: A third significant challenge comes out from both grammatical and syntactic sides. Typology shows that languages belong to different structural types: analytic languages like English rely heavily on word order, while agglutinative languages like Uzbek rely on suffixes and inflections. This difference creates difficulties when translating complex sentences. For instance, an English sentence “The story I read last night was pretty engaging” uses relative clauses directly, whereas in Uzbek the structure and word order changes when we want to talk “Kecha o’qigan hikoyam juda qiziqarli edi” A direct word-for-word translation seems to be so useless at that time. This explains like “languages which rich morphology, such as agglutinative languages, tend to prefer non-finite verb forms like participles for relativization, instead of relative pronouns as in English” [T. Givonn, 1990; 541]

Typological research by Comrie and Dryer has shown that relative clauses, tense-aspect markers, and word order patterns shows difference widely in different languages. Translators must be aware of these structural differences to avoid distortions in meaning.

The study has shown that comparative typology plays a significant role in understanding and solving translation problems. At the heart of this relationship lies the tension between universality and cultural diversity. On the one hand, semantic universals identified by Greenberg, Wierzbicka, and others create a shared foundation that makes translation possible across languages. They allow translators to capture core human experiences in different linguistic systems. On the other hand, the limits of these universals reveal the complexity of cultural variation, where even basic categories like color or kinship can shift in meaning from one language to another.

Finally, structural differences between languages were examined as another major source of difficulty. The contrast between analytic and agglutinative systems, or the different ways languages construct relative clauses, illustrates how typological variation directly affects translation. The solution lies in syntactic adaptation, which allows translators to preserve meaning while adjusting structures to fit the natural grammar of the target language. Corpus-based studies confirm that this adaptation is not an exception but a necessary practice in professional translation.

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MNEMOTEXNIKA ASOSIDA INGLIZ TILINI O‘QITISHNING SAMARALI USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o‘qitishda mnemotexnika (xotira texnikasi) usullaridan foydalanishning samaradorligi ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot davomida mnemotexnik metodlarning o‘quvchilarda so‘z boyligini oshirish, grammatik ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirish, talaffuzni yaxshilash hamda o‘quvchilarning motivatsiyasini kuchaytirishdagi ahamiyati ko‘rsatib berilgan. Shuningdek, mnemotexnik yondashuvlarning psixologik va didaktik asoslari, zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan uyg‘unlashuvi ham yoritilgan. Natijada, mnemotexnika ingliz tilini o‘rgatishda o‘quvchilarning eslab qolish darajasini sezilarli darajada oshiruvchi samarali usul ekanligi isbotlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Mnemotexnika, ingliz tili, ta‘lim texnologiyasi, metodika, xotira, innovatsiya, til o‘qitish, eslab qolish.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida chet tillarini, ayniqsa ingliz tilini mukammal o‘rganish nafaqat kasbiy, balki ijtimoiy ehtiyojga aylanib bormoqda. Ta‘lim tizimida ingliz tili o‘qitish metodlarini takomillashtirish - o‘quvchilarning xotira, diqqat, tafakkur va ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantiruvchi muhim omillardan biridir. An‘anaviy yodlash usullari ko‘p hollarda o‘quvchini charchatadi, natijada o‘rganilgan so‘zlar tezda unutiladi. Shu bois, o‘qitish jarayonida mnemotexnika usullaridan foydalanish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalaga aylandi.

Mnemotexnika - bu ma‘lumotlarni yodlash va eslab qolishni osonlashtiruvchi maxsus metodlar tizimi bo‘lib, u inson xotirasining tabiiy imkoniyatlarini faollashtiradi. Ingliz tili darslarida bu texnika yordamida o‘quvchilar yangi so‘z va iboralarni obrazlar, tasvirlar, tovushlar, harakatlar yoki hissiyotlar bilan bog‘lab o‘rganadilar. Natijada, bilimlar uzoq muddatli xotirada saqlanadi va muloqot jarayonida faol qo‘llanadi.

Mnemotexnika atamasi yunoncha “mneme” (xotira) so‘zidan kelib chiqqan. Uning tarixiy ildizlari qadimiy Yunoniston davriga borib taqaladi. Dastlab bu usul notiqlik san‘atida nutqni eslab qolish uchun qo‘llanilgan. Hozirda esa u ta‘lim, psixologiya va lingvistika sohalarida keng qo‘llanilmoqda.

Ta‘lim jarayonida mnemotexnika - o‘quvchining eslab qolish mexanizmini faollashtiruvchi texnologiya sifatida qaraladi. O‘quvchilarda yangi ma‘lumotni o‘zlashtirish ko‘rsatkichini oshiradi, tafakkurni kengaytiradi va o‘rganilayotgan tilga nisbatan qiziqishni kuchaytiradi. Psixologlar fikricha, inson eshitgan ma‘lumotning 20 foizini, ko‘rganining 40 foizini, ammo ko‘rib, eshitib va amalda bajarganining 90 foizini eslab qoladi. Demak, mnemotexnika bu uchta faoliyatni birlashtiradi.

Mnemotexnika o‘quvchilarda quyidagi ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantiradi:
xotira hajmini kengaytiradi;

- ✓ soʻzlarni tez eslab qolish va chaqirish qobiliyatini oshiradi;
- ✓ oʻrganilgan bilimlarni tizimlashtiradi;
- ✓ mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi;
- ✓ nutq faoliyatini mustahkamlaydi.

Ingliz tilini oʻrganish jarayonida mnemotexnik usullar turlicha shaklda qoʻllanilishi mumkin. Quyida ularning eng samaralilari haqida batafsil toʻxtalamiz.

1. Soʻzlarni assotsiatsiya orqali yodlash: Bu usulda yangi soʻz maʼnosi oʻquvchiga tanish narsa bilan bogʻlanadi. Masalan, “rainbow” soʻzini “rain” (yomgʻir) va “bow” (kamon) soʻzlari bilan bogʻlash orqali oʻquvchi uni yaxlit obraz sifatida eslab qoladi. “Chair” soʻzini esa “chaqaloq oʻtiradigan joy” deb assotsiatsiya qilish mumkin. Shu tarzda soʻz va maʼno oʻrtasida mustahkam aloqa hosil boʻladi.

2. Vizual obrazlar yordamida oʻqitish: Oʻquvchilarga yangi soʻzlar rasmlar, belgilar yoki piktogrammalar orqali taqdim etiladi. Masalan, “sleep” – yostiq rasmi, “eat” – likopcha, “run” – yugurayotgan odam rasmi. Koʻrish orqali oʻrganilgan maʼlumot uzoq muddatli xotirada saqlanadi.

3. Qisqa sheʼrlar va ritmik mnemokodlar: Grammatika qoidalarini oson eslab qolish uchun ritmik jumlar yoki qisqa sheʼrlar ishlatiladi. Masalan: He, she, it - takes ‘s’ in it.

Bu kichik mnemokod oʻquvchiga uchinchi shaxs birlikdagi feʼlga “-s” qoʻshilishi qoidasi haqida eslatma boʻlib xizmat qiladi. Bunday ritmik ifodalar grammatikani yodda saqlashni osonlashtiradi.

4. Hikoya va voqealar orqali oʻrganish: Soʻzlar maʼnosini yodlashdan tashqari, ularni kichik hikoyalar tarkibida ishlatish juda samarali. Masalan, “cat”, “mouse”, “milk”, “table” soʻzlarini bir voqea shaklida berish (“The cat drinks milk on the table”) oʻquvchilarga mazmunni yaxshiroq anglash va eslab qolish imkonini beradi.

5. Raqamli mnemotexnika: Bugungi raqamli davrda mobil ilovalar (Anki, Quizlet, Memrise) mnemotexnik prinsiplar asosida ishlab chiqilgan. Bu platformalarda soʻzlar rasmlar, audio, tarjima va testlar bilan birgalikda taklif etiladi. Takrorlash intervali tizimi orqali oʻrganilgan soʻzlar muntazam mustahkamlanadi.

6. Xotira xaritalari (Mind maps): Bu usulda oʻquvchilar soʻzlar va gʻoyalarni tarmoqli shaklda joylashtiradilar. Masalan, “Food” markaziy soʻzidan “fruit”, “meat”, “vegetables”, “drinks” kabi tarmoqlar ajratiladi. Bu usul mantiqiy bogʻlanishlarni yaratib, mavzuni yaxlit koʻrinishda idrok etishga yordam beradi.

7. Emotsional mnemotexnika: Soʻz yoki ibora hissiyot bilan bogʻlanganida, u ongda kuchliroq saqlanadi. Masalan, oʻqituvchi “happy” soʻzini ifodalashda oʻquvchilarga tabassum qilishni soʻrasa, bu hissiy aloqa orqali soʻz mustahkam yodda qoladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, mnemotexnika ingliz tilini oʻrgatishda oʻquvchilarning yodlash, eslab qolish, nutqni shakllantirish hamda mustaqil oʻrganish koʻnikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi samarali metoddir. U oʻquvchi ongida obrazli, hissiy va mantiqiy aloqalarni yaratish orqali bilimni mustahkamlaydi.

Mnemotexnika nafaqat xotirani, balki ijodkorlikni, tafakkurni va muloqot koʻnikmalarini ham rivojlantiradi. Shu bois, uni zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar bilan uygʻunlashtirish oʻqitish sifatini yangi bosqichga koʻtaradi. Ingliz tilini oʻrganishda mnemotexnika asosidagi metodlardan foydalanish bugungi taʼlim jarayonining ajralmas qismiga aylanishi zarur.

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BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA CHET TILLARINI O'QITISHDA ONA TILINING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida chet tillarini o'qitishda ona tilining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati yoritilgan. O'quvchilarning lingvistik tafakkurini shakllantirishda, chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida ona tili asosida taqqoslash va qiyoslash metodlaridan foydalanishning samarali jihatlari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, chet tili, kompetensiya, innovatsiya, ona tili, o'zbek tili, muloqot, madaniyatlararo.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida xorijiy tillarni o'rganish zaruriy ehtiyojga aylanmoqda. Shu bilan birga, chet tili o'qitish jarayonida ona tili tayanch va vosita sifatida muhim o'rin tutadi. Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tillarini o'qitish o'quvchilarda nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini, balki madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasini ham shakllantiradi. Chet tillarini o'qitishda ona tili muhimdir. Biz bu orqali bolalarda solishtirish ko'nikmasini shakllantiramiz. Boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida chet tilini o'qitish jarayonida ona tilining o'rni beqiyosdir. Chunki bola til o'rganishni aynan ona tili orqali boshlaydi, tildagi asosiy tushunchalar, grammatik tuzilmalar, talaffuz va so'z boyligi haqidagi ilk bilimlar ham ona tili asosida shakllanadi.

Asosiy qism. Ona tili har bir o'quvchining tilda fikrlash, tushunish va o'z fikrini ifodalashga o'rgatuvchi asosiy vositadir. Shuning uchun chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida o'quvchi ona tilidagi bilimlariga tayanadi. Masalan, so'z tartibi, grammatik shakllar, talaffuz va ma'no mosliklarini taqqoslash orqali yangi tilni o'zlashtirish osonlashadi. O'qituvchi chet tili darslarini ona tilidagi grammatik tushunchalar bilan bog'lagan holda olib borsa, o'quvchilarda tilning ichki tuzilishi, morfologik va sintaktik xususiyatlariga nisbatan chuqurroq tushuncha shakllanadi. Shu bilan birga, o'quvchilar lingvistik tafakkurini rivojlantirish, tahlil qilish, taqqoslash va umumlashtirish ko'nikmalarini egallaydilar. Ona tili asosida chet tilini o'qitishning yana bir afzalligi o'quvchilarning psixologik tayyorgarligini mustahkamlashdir. Chet tili ular uchun mutlaqo yangi tizim bo'lgani sababli, ona tilidagi tushunchalar orqali uni tushuntirish dars jarayonini yengillashtiradi va motivatsiyani oshiradi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari hali til tizimi haqida to'liq tasavvurga ega emaslar. Shu sababli ular chet tilini o'rganishda mavjud ona tili bilimlariga tayanadilar. O'qituvchi yangi til elementlarini (masalan, ot, fe'l, sifat, gap tuzilishi) ona tilidagi o'xshash yoki farqli jihatlar bilan solishtirib tushuntirganda, o'quvchilar materialni osonroq o'zlashtiradilar. Ingliz tilidagi "I am a pupil" gapini o'rgatishda o'qituvchi "Men o'quvchiman" degan ona tilidagi gap bilan

qiyoslab, fe'ning o'rnini, bog'lovchi so'zning funksiyasini tushuntiradi. Ona tilidan foydalanish o'quvchiga til hodisalarini taqqoslash imkonini beradi. Shu orqali bola grammatik qoidalarni mexanik yod olish o'rniga, ularning mazmunini chuqurroq anglaydi. Masalan, ingliz tilida so'z tartibi qat'iy ekanini o'quvchi o'zbek tilidagi erkin so'z tartibi bilan taqqoslab bilib oladi. Chet tilidagi yangi so'zlarni o'rganishda ularning ona tilidagi tarjimalari va sinonimlarini bilish so'z boyligini kengaytiradi. Shu tariqa o'quvchi nafaqat chet tilida, balki ona tilida ham so'z zaxirasini boyitadi.

Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tilini o'qitishda ona tilining o'rni beqiyosdir. Ona tili yordamida o'quvchi chet tilini mantiqan, grammatik jihatdan va leksik jihatdan to'g'ri o'zlashtiradi. Shunday ekan, o'qituvchi dars jarayonida ona tili va chet tili o'rtasidagi uzviy bog'liqlikni hisobga olgan holda, integrativ yondashuv asosida ishlasa, bu til o'rganish samaradorligini oshiradi. Boshlang'ich ta'limda chet tilini o'qitishda ona tilining o'rni juda muhim bo'lib, u o'quvchining yangi tilni o'zlashtirishida tayanch asos vazifasini bajaradi. Chet tili darslarida ona tili orqali o'quvchilarda til hodisalarini tushunish, grammatik qoidalarni taqqoslash va mantiqiy fikrlash ko'nikmalari shakllanadi. Ona tili yordamida chet tilidagi so'z va iboralarni osonroq tushunish, ularni eslab qolish va to'g'ri talaffuz qilish imkoniyati kengayadi. Shu bilan birga, o'quvchi ikki tilda so'zlashish madaniyatini rivojlantiradi, bu esa uning nutqiy, mantiqiy va kommunikativ salohiyatini oshiradi.

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SOCIOLINGUISTICS AND CULTURAL CONTEXT IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Anotation: This article investigates the significant role of sociolinguistics and cultural context in the process of language learning. It explains how social interactions, cultural values, and communication patterns shape the learner's understanding and use of language. The paper highlights that language is not only a linguistic system but also a social and cultural phenomenon that reflects people's identities and beliefs. It discusses how awareness of sociolinguistic factors such as register, dialect, and communicative style helps learners use language more appropriately in real-life contexts. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of integrating cultural content into language education to develop learners' intercultural competence, tolerance, and communicative effectiveness. Understanding the sociolinguistic and cultural aspects of language enhances both teaching and learning outcomes, fostering meaningful communication in a globalized world.

Keywords: Sociolinguistics, cultural context, language learning, intercultural communication, communicative competence.

The study of a foreign language involves much more than simply mastering grammar rules or learning new vocabulary. In our globalized society, the ability to adapt language use to different cultural and social settings has become a crucial skill. Learners are often required to interact with individuals from various backgrounds, which makes it necessary to understand both linguistic accuracy and cultural appropriateness. This paper examines the importance of sociolinguistics and cultural context in the process of language learning. It

argues that language competence cannot be achieved without taking into account the social factors that influence communication and the cultural norms that define meaning. Unlike traditional approaches that treat language as a set of structural rules, this perspective views it as a living tool shaped by society and culture.

Sociolinguistics is concerned with how language functions within society and how it varies depending on factors such as age, gender, class, and geographical location. For language learners, this knowledge is extremely valuable. It allows them to recognize that no language is entirely uniform; instead, it is made up of multiple varieties and styles that serve different purposes. For example, students must learn to distinguish between formal and informal registers. In English, phrases such as 'Good morning, sir' may be suitable for professional environments, whereas 'Hey, what's up?' is more appropriate for informal conversations. Failure to recognize such distinctions can lead to misunderstandings or even unintended disrespect. Another aspect is the link between language and identity. The way individuals speak often reveals their social background, regional affiliation, or group membership. By studying these relationships, learners not only gain communicative competence but also develop a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity.

Language and culture are inseparable; one cannot be fully understood without the other. Every linguistic expression carries cultural meanings that reflect the values and traditions of the community where it is used. Without this awareness, learners risk misinterpreting messages or using language in ways that may seem inappropriate to native speakers. Consider greetings: in many English-speaking societies, 'How are you?' often functions as a polite expression rather than a genuine inquiry.

However, in other cultures, such a question may invite a detailed response. Learners who do not recognize these cultural differences may find themselves confused in everyday interactions. Non-verbal communication is another area strongly tied to culture. Body language, gestures, and even silence can carry different meanings across societies. For instance, direct eye contact may signal confidence in Western cultures, while in some Asian contexts it can be perceived as disrespectful. Understanding these subtleties is just as important as mastering spoken language.

Pragmatic competence also relies on cultural context. The way people apologize, refuse requests, or show politeness varies from culture to culture. Thus, learners must be trained not only in language forms but also in the cultural norms that guide their use.

Given the importance of sociolinguistic and cultural awareness, language teaching must go beyond structural competence. Teachers can adopt several methods to ensure that learners acquire both linguistic and intercultural skills. First, the use of authentic materials such as films, songs, online articles, and television programs provides learners with exposure to real-life communication. These resources demonstrate how language is naturally used in society, offering valuable insights into both speech patterns and cultural references. Second, role-playing activities and classroom simulations allow students to practice communication in realistic contexts. By enacting scenarios like job interviews, business meetings, or friendly conversations, learners gain confidence and develop the ability to adjust their speech to different situations. Third, intercultural comparisons are highly beneficial. Students can discuss similarities and differences between their own culture and that of the target language. Such reflection not only promotes understanding but also reduces the risk of cultural misunderstandings. Finally, sociolinguistic exercises such as analyzing dialogues for levels of politeness or comparing regional dialects encourage learners to notice language variation. This practice strengthens their adaptability and helps them communicate effectively in diverse environments.

In summary, successful language learning requires attention not only to grammar and vocabulary but also to the social and cultural dimensions of language. Sociolinguistics equips learners with the ability to recognize variation and choose appropriate registers, while cultural context teaches them how to interpret meanings and behave appropriately in different communities. When language education integrates these elements, students develop both communicative and intercultural competence. They become capable of avoiding misunderstandings, building stronger relationships, and participating confidently in cross-cultural interactions. Thus, the role of sociolinguistics and cultural awareness in language learning cannot be underestimated. These aspects ensure that learners are not only accurate in their speech but also effective, respectful, and adaptive communicators in our increasingly interconnected world.

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SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING XORIJIY TILLARNI O'RGANISHDAGI ROLI, IMKONIYATLARI, MUAMMOLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonidagi roli va ta'siri chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Asosiy e'tibor sun'iy intellekt yordamida shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim imkoniyatlariga, interaktiv o'quv vositalariga, madaniyatlararo muloqotga tayangan o'quv mihitini yaratishdagi afzalliklarga qaratilgan. Maqolada ChatGpt, Duolingo va Elsa Speak kabi mashhur ilovalar misolida texnologiyalarning qanday ishlashi va amaliy yordami ko'rsatiladi. Sun'iy intellikning til o'rganishdagi ustoz bilan integratsiyasi, imkoniyat va cheklovlari nazariy hamda amaliy nuqtai nazardan o'rganilgan. Shuningdek maqolada kelajakdagi ilmiy loyihalarga oid g'oyalar, xususan SI yordamida o'quv platformasi yaratish rejalari ham ilgari surilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, xorijiy tillarni o'rganish, madaniyatlararo muloqot, individuallashtirilgan ta'lim, ta'limiy texnologiyalar

Abstract: This article provides an in-depth analysis of the role and impact of artificial intelligence technologies in the process of learning foreign languages. The main focus is on personalized learning opportunities enabled by AI, interactive educational tools, and the advantages of creating a learning environment based on intercultural communication. The article illustrates the practical use and functioning of popular applications such as ChatGPT, Duolingo, and Elsa Speak. The integration of artificial intelligence with human instructors, as well as the theoretical and practical possibilities and limitations of AI in language learning,

are examined. Additionally, future scientific project ideas, including plans to develop an AI-powered learning platform, are proposed.

Key words: artificial intelligent, learning foreign languages, intercultural communication, personalized education, educational technology

Zamonaviy dunyoda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish ko'plab sohalarda, jumladan ta'lim, biznes, ilm-fan va madaniyatlararo muloqotda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Globalizatsiya jarayonida ko'p tillilik va madaniyatlararo tushunish insonlarning kasbiy va shaxsiy rivojlanishida asosiy omillardan biriga aylangan. Shu sababli, til o'rganish jarayonini samarali va qulay qilishga qaratilgan texnologiyalar, xususan sun'iy intellekt (SI) tizimlari, yuksak e'tirof etilmoqda. Sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi so'nggi yutuqlar ta'lim tizimida yangi imkoniyatlar yaratib, individuallashtirilgan, interaktiv va o'quvchining ehtiyojlariga moslashgan ta'lim usullarini taqdim etmoqda. Xususan, til o'rganish jarayonida SI asosida ishlovchi chatbotlar, avtomatik tarjima tizimlari, talaffuzni yaxshilash vositalari va boshqa ilg'or texnologiyalar samaradorlikni oshirmoqda.

Sun'iy intellektning til o'rganishdagi roli va imkoniyatlari: Zamonaviy ta'limda sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonini tubdan o'zgartirmoqda. SI yordamida ta'lim shaxsiylashtirilgan, interaktiv va o'quvchining individual ehtiyojlariga moslashgan holga kelmoqda. Bu texnologiyalar an'anaviy darslik va mashg'ulotlardan farqli o'laroq, til o'rganishni samaraliroq, qiziqarli va oson qiladi.

SI ilovalari va ularning amaliy yordami: Bugungi kunda til o'rganishda eng ommabop SI ilovalaridan biri – Duolingo. Ushbu platforma o'quvchilarning har biriga individual yondashgan holda, yoshi, bilim darajasi va o'rganish sur'ati asosida shaxsiy ta'lim dasturlarini tuzadi. Duolingo o'yinlashtirilgan metodlarni qo'llab, foydalanuvchilarni doimiy ravishda rag'batlantiradi va ularning til o'rganishga qiziqishini oshiradi. Shuningdek, tizim olingan natijalar asosida qaysi sohalarga ko'proq e'tibor qaratish kerakligini aniqlaydi. Elsa Speak ilovasi esa asosan talaffuz bilan shug'ullanadi. Bu dastur foydalanuvchining nutqini SI yordamida tahlil qiladi, talaffuzdagi xatolarni aniqlaydi va aniq tavsiyalar beradi. Natijada, foydalanuvchilar chet tilidagi talaffuzga yaqinroq gapirish ko'nikmasiga ega bo'ladilar.

Yana bir ilg'or vosita – ChatGPT kabi sun'iy intellektga asoslangan interaktiv chatbotlar. Bu SI yordamchilar bilan foydalanuvchilar erkin muloqot qilishi, savollar berishi, yozma va og'zaki mashqlar bajarishi mumkin. ChatGPT tilni amaliyotda qo'llash, yangi iboralar va grammatik qoidalarni o'rganishda katta yordam beradi. Tandem, Hello Talk kabi ilovalar orqali real insonlar bilan muloqot qilish orqali suhbat qura olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish mumkin. Memrise ilovasi orqali so'zlarni kontekstda eslab qolishga yo'naltirilgan mashg'ulotlar orqali so'zlarni tez fursatda o'rganish imkoniyatini beradi.

Yuqorida nomi qayd etilgan texnologiyalar til o'rganishda quyidagi afzalliklarni taqdim etadi:

- ✓ Individuallashtirilgan ta'lim: Har bir o'quvchining ehtiyojlari va qobiliyatlariga mos darslar tuziladi.
- ✓ Faollik: Foydalanuvchilar bir vaqtning o'zida mashqlar bajaradi va savollarga javob oladi.
- ✓ Qulaylik: Istalgan vaqtda, har qanday joyda til o'rganish olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lish.
- ✓ Ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish: O'quvchilarning kuchli va zaif tomonlari aniqlanib, ta'lim jarayoni yanada optimallashtiriladi.
- ✓ Madaniyatlararo muloqot: AI yordamida turli tillar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi farqlar va o'xshashliklar yaxshiroq tushuniladi.

Shunga qaramay, SI texnologiyalaridan foydalanishda bir nechta cheklovlar va muammolarga duch kelinmoqda. Masalan:

- ✓ Emotsional va ijtimoiy jihatlar: SI ustozning hissiy qo'llab-quvvatlashi va motivatsiyasini to'liq taqlid qila olmaydi. Bu esa o'z navbatida, o'quvchida motivatsiyani yo'qolishiga sabab bo'lishi mumkin
- ✓ Kontekstual tushuncha: SI ba'zan murakkab kontekstlarni to'liq anglamasligi mumkin.
- ✓ Texnik cheklovlar: Ba'zi bir chekka hududlarda internetga bog'lanish bilan muammolar mavjudligi bois, ular bu imkoniyatlar foydalanishda qiynchiliklarga duch kelishmoqda.

Yuqoridagi muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun SI va insonning birgalikdagi faoliyati muhim hisoblanadi. Ustozlar SI vositalarini qo'llab, o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlariga yanada moslashgan yondashuvni ta'minlashlari mumkin. Shu bilan birga, ustozlar murakkab tushunchalarni tushuntirish, motivatsiyani oshirish va madaniy jihatlarni chuqurroq tushuntirishda davom etadilar. Sun'iy intellekt asosida ishlaydigan o'quv platformalar yaratish istiqbollarga oid loyihalar ustida ishlar davom etmoqda. Masalan, o'quvchilarning qobiliyatlarini doimiy monitoring qilish, real vaqt rejimida individual maslahatlar berish va hatto virtual haqiqat (VR) texnologiyalari bilan til o'rgatish tizimlarini rivojlantirish ko'zda tutilmoqda.

Kelajakdagi loyihalar istiqbollari: Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlarini kengroq tadbiiq etish maqsadida kelajakda quyidagi yo'nalishlarda loyiha ustida ishlash rejalashtirilmoqda:

1. SI asosida O'zbekcha–Inglizcha interaktiv platforma yaratish. Ushbu platforma orqali foydalanuvchining bilim darajasini tahlil qilinib, individual mashqlar va tavsiyalar taqdim etiladi. Talaffuzni baholash tizimi ham kiritiladi.
2. SI yordamida o'zbek tilini xorijliklarga o'rgatishga mo'ljallangan mobil ilova ishlab chiqish. Bu ilova o'zbek tili va madaniyatini tanishtiruvchi interaktiv mashqlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Mashqlarni bajarish davomida foydalanuvchilar o'zbek xalqining urf odatlari, buyuk ajdodlarimiz hayoti va ijodi haqida qiziqarli faktlar va ular ijodlaridan parchalar haqida ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishadi.
3. Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'rganish algoritmlarini ishlab chiqish. Foydalanuvchi faoliyatiga qarab sun'iy intellekt unga eng mos o'quv materiallarini tavsiya qiladi. Hozircha bu g'oyalar dastlabki bosqichda, ammo ularni amalda sinab ko'rish va tadqiqotga aylantirish niyati mavjud. Mazkur maqola ushbu loyihalar uchun ilmiy poydevor bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning o'rni tobora ortib bormoqda. Duolingo, Elsa Speak, ChatGPT, Memrise kabi vositalar til o'rganish jarayonini interaktiv va shaxsiylashtirilgan tarzda olib borishga yordam bermoqda. Ular foydalanuvchining til kompetensiyasini tahlil qilib, u bilan samarali ishlay oladi. Shunga qaramay, AI texnologiyalari inson ustozining hissiy, madaniy va pedagogik yondashuvlarini to'liq almashtira olmaydi. Shu sababli eng yaxshi natija sun'iy intellekt vositalari va ustoz faoliyatining uyg'unligida ko'zga tashlanadi. Kelajakda ushbu texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda yangi ta'lim loyihalarini yaratish va ilmiy izlanishlarni davom ettirish rejalashtirilmoqda. Mazkur maqola esa shu yo'nalishdagi dastlabki nazariy yondashuv sifatida baholanishi mumkin.

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INGLIZ TILI O'QITISH METODIKASI VA O'ZBEK TILI BILAN UYG'UNLASHUVI

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***Anotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'qitish yo'lida qo'llaniladigan turli xil metod va texnikalar haqida bayon qilingan. Shu bilan birga ingliz tilini o'rganishga qo'llaniladigan yordamchi vositalarni o'zbek tili bilan qiyoslab uyg'unlashishi muhokama qilingan. Bundan tashqari maqolada o'rganish yo'lida duch keladigan muammolar, taklif etilgan yechimlar hamda rivojlanish yo'llari ko'rib chiqilgan. O'rganuvchilarga o'rganishda muhim bo'lgan yondashuvlari va metodologik jihatdan taqdim etish yo'li bilan, qolaversa yqxshi natijaga yetishish yo'lidagi harakat va ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish asosiy maqsad hisoblanadi. Shuningdek, metodikaning shakllanishiga o'z hissasini qo'shgan shaxslar, olim, professorlar ham ko'rib o'tilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** ingliz tili, metodika, texnika, yondashuvlar, dars ko'nikmasi, olimlar, professorlar, CLT, TBLT, Natural approach, audio lingual metod, grammatika, tarjima qilish, TESOL.*

Abstract: In this article, various methods and techniques used in the process of teaching English in Uzbekistan are described. At the same time, the integration of auxiliary tools applied in learning English with the Uzbek language is discussed. In addition, the article examines the problems encountered in the process of learning, the proposed solutions, as well as the ways of development. The main goal is to develop learners' approaches and methodological ways of presentation that are important in learning, as well as to foster efforts and skills aimed at achieving good results. Moreover, the article also reviews the individuals, scholars, and professors who contributed to the formation of methodology.

Keywords: English, method, technique, approaches, lesson skills, scientists, professors, CLT, TBLT, Natural approach, audio-lingual metod, grammar, translation, tesol.

Ingliz tilini o'rganish uchun katta katta imkoniyatlar mavjud bo'lsada, bu yo'lda bir nechta muammolar ham uchraydi. xx asr va xxi asr boshlarida ingliz tilini o'qilishda an'anaviy usul ya'ni so'zlarni yodlash hamda tarjima metodikasidan ko'ra, so'zlashish va muloqot usullari uchun o'ziga xo'sh metodikalar ishlab chiqildi va o'qitish boshlandi. dastlabki metod bu communicative language teaching (clt) bo'lib, bu metod gramatikadan ozgina uzoqlashib asosan hayotiy muloqot vositasi sifatida o'qilishga e'tibor beradi. shu bilan birga task-based language teaching (tblt) metodi ham mavjud bo'lib, u nazariy o'qishdan chetlashib, amaliy usulda ya'ni asosan nutqqa xos topshiriqlar bilan ingliz tilini o'rganishdir. keyingi metod bu

direct method va natural approach bo'lib, ingliz tilini tabiiy muhit bilan o'rganish hisoblansa, yan bir metod audio-lingual metod bo'lib, tillarni tinglab tushinish hamda takrorlash orqali o'rganishdir. bu bilan til ko'nikmasi avtomatik tarzda yaxshilanadi. lekin ba'zi maktablarda hali hamon grammar translation method ya'ni eski metodlar qo'llanilib kelinmoqda. zamonaviy metodlarni eskilaridan farqi shundaki, yangi metodlar darsda qo'llanilsa, dars jarayonida barcha o'quvchilar faol bola oladi, speaking skillariga ham yordam beradi hamda amaliy til bilish uchun yo'nalganligi bilan farqlanib turadi. lekin bu metodlarni o'zbekistonning ta'lim tizimida qo'llashda bir nechta muammolar yuzasidan muhokama qilsak:

til o'rganishga muhit yetishmasligi- o'quvchilarning maktabda boshqa tilda muloqot qilish imkoniyati ma'lum darajada cheklanib qolgan.

metodika resusrlarining kamligi- clt va tblt metodikalari uchun kerakli bo'lgan qo'llanmalar va darsliklar to'liq ishlab chiqilmagan.

o'qituvchilarning malaka darajalari- bu metodlar kirib kelishi yoki ishlab chiqilganiga ko'p vaqt bo'lmadi hamda shundan kelib chiqadiki, pedagog kadrlar ham malakaga to'liq ega emas. bu esa bilim darajasiga salbiy ta'sir qilmasdan qolmaydi.

sinfdagi o'quvchi sonining ko'pligi- o'zbek maktablarida bir sinfdan 30tadan 40tagacha sinf bo'lganligi uchun 40minut dars davomida har bir o'quvchi bilan individual ishlash qiyinchilik olib keladi.

Shuning uchun ham ingliz tilining metodikasini ishlab chiqishda yuqori tajribalarni shu bilan birga o'zbek ta'lim tizimiga moslashgan holda ishlab chiqish zaruriyati mavjud va bu dolzarb ham vazifa ham muammo bo'lmoqda.

Til o'rganishdagi metodikani o'zbek ta'lim tizimiga foydali bo'lishi uchun ilmiy jamiyatlar, davlat siyosati hamda albatta o'qituvchilar katta hissalarini qo'shishadi. Yurtimizda kelasi yillarda bolalarga til o'rgatishda erta yoshdan boshlab o'qitish rejalari mavjud. Prezident qarorlari asosan maktabgacha ta'limdan boshlab til o'rgatish yo'lga qo'yilgan hamda bu metodikalarni o'zgartirishga olib keldi. Metodika deyilganda faqat xorijiy metodlarni tushinish xato bo'ladi va an'anaviy metodlar ham ishlab chiqilmoqda. Misol uchun CLT, TBLT metodlari o'zbek ta'lim tizimiga moshlatirishda ko'plab metodistlar va olim, professorlar xizmat qolishmoqda. Bularning natijasida esa ingliz tili o'qitishda yangi usullarni qo'llash orqali o'rganuvchilarni darsga jalb qiloladi. Yurtimiz ta'lim shaklida bu usullarni qo'llash uchun moslashtirish kerak va bu yo'ldagi aytib o'tilgan muammolar o'z yechimini asta bartaraf etmoqda. Shu bilan birga davlat siyosati, xalqlar are hamkorliklar va o'qituvchilarning xizmatlari natijasida ingliz tili metodikalari soni kengayib bormoqda.

Metodikalarni ishlab chiqishda turli olimlar, professorlar va o'qituvchilar hikmat qilishgan. O'zbek professorlaridan Sh. Rahmatullayev ingliz tili tilshunosligida hamda ko'plab metodikalar ishlab chiqish bo'yicha mashhurdir. Professor G. Abdurahmonova ham tillarni o'qitish metodikasi va tarjima nazariyalari bo'yicha ko'plab izlanishlar olib borgan va ko'p til o'qitish to'g'risidagi maqola va ilmiy ishlarda bu shaxsning nomlarini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Dotsent M. Yoqubova ingliz tilini o'rgatishda kommunikativ metodlarni ko'rsatib bera olgan. Bundan tashqari Xorijiy o'qituvchilar ham tillarni o'qitish bo'yicha mashhurdir. Misol qilib, Noam Chomskiy generativ gramatika nazariyasi orqali o'rganuvchining til o'rganishdagi tug'ma qobiyatini asoslagan. Stephen Krashen narural approach nazariyasi bo'yicha til o'rganishda tabiiy muhit va tushunarlilik bir asosiy omil sifatida ko'radi. Yana bir olim Michael Long TBLT metodikasiga o'zining katta hissasini qo'shgan.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsam, umuman olganda ingliz tilini o'rgatishda yangi ishlab chiqilgan metod, usullardan foydalanish o'quvchilar uchun faqat nazariy bilim emas,

o'zlarining hayotiy yo'lida kerak bo'ladigan amaliy muloqot ko'nikmasini ham organadi. O'zbek ta'lim tizimida bu kabi yondashuvlari amalga oshirish uchun malaka darajasiga ega bo'lgan o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, o'qitish, shu bilan birga yaxshi sifatga ega bo'lgan darsliklarni yaratish, ham zamonaviylashgan texnologiyalardan doimiy foydalanish ta'lim tizimining rivoji uchun katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Bundan tashqari metodika bo'yicha kerakli resurslarni topshiriqlar yoki ularni kengaytirish uchun xalqaro tashkilotlarning (Britaniya va Amerika kengashi, TESOL) elektron platformalaridan foydalanish mumkin. Bunda chet elning ilmiy resurslarini milliy ta'lim sharoitiga o'girishda ham foydalanilsa bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari onlayn kurslar, ochiq bo'lgan ilmiy manbalar ham o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar uchun qo'shimcha manba deb qarash mumkin. Shunday qilib, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda metodika va texnikalarni kengaytirish, manbalarning sonini oshirish orqali ta'lim sifatini sezilarli tarzda o'zgartirish mumkin.

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DIGITAL LITERACY AND TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of digital literacy and modern technologies in language learning. It emphasizes the importance of developing students' digital skills for effective communication, online collaboration, and autonomous learning. The paper also explores digital tools, platforms, and strategies that enhance motivation and efficiency in foreign language acquisition.

Keywords: digital literacy, technology, language learning, online tools, motivation, communication, innovation.

In the 21st century, technology has become an inseparable part of human life, influencing every sphere of society, including education. The process of language learning has undergone significant transformation due to the rapid development of digital technologies. Digital literacy is no longer an additional skill but a necessary component for successful communication and lifelong learning. Language learning is not limited to traditional textbooks and classroom interactions anymore. Digital technologies such as computers, smartphones, and the Internet provide learners with access to a variety of resources and global communication opportunities. According to researchers, students who possess strong digital literacy skills are more capable of engaging with authentic materials, collaborating online, and developing critical thinking. Digital literacy refers to the ability to use digital tools, platforms, and technologies effectively and responsibly. It includes not only technical skills

but also cognitive and social competencies such as evaluating online information, creating digital content, and maintaining online ethics. As Bawden (2008) noted, digital literacy combines traditional literacy, information literacy, and ICT literacy. In the context of language learning, digital literacy enables students to navigate multimedia materials, use online dictionaries, participate in digital discussions, and express their thoughts in diverse formats. Technology has revolutionized the way languages are taught and learned. It provides interactive, engaging, and personalized learning experiences. Some of the key benefits include: 1. Access to authentic materials. 2. Online communication tools. 3. Language learning applications. 4. Social media and forums. 5. Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools.

Motivation is one of the key factors in successful language acquisition. Digital tools increase students' engagement by making learning more interactive and meaningful. Visual and audio materials capture learners' attention, while online games and quizzes make practice enjoyable. Moreover, learners can track their progress, set goals, and receive instant feedback - all of which enhance motivation. Despite the advantages, there are also certain challenges in integrating technology into language learning: - Lack of digital competence among teachers and students. - Technical issues such as poor Internet connection or limited access to devices. - Information overload due to excessive online materials. - Digital distraction, which may decrease concentration.

Practical applications and pedagogical recommendations: Teachers should integrate technology in a meaningful way by: 1. Using multimedia tasks such as video projects or digital storytelling. 2. Encouraging students to participate in online discussions and collaborative writing. 3. Employing Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle or Google Classroom. 4. Training students to evaluate online sources critically. 5. Promoting blended and hybrid learning environments.

Digital literacy and technology play an essential role in modern language education. They transform traditional teaching into a dynamic, interactive, and learner-centered process. By integrating digital tools, educators can foster autonomy, motivation, and global communication skills. However, successful implementation requires not only access to technology but also continuous development of digital competence among teachers and learners. In the modern era, technology plays a vital role in almost every aspect of human life, including education. One of the most significant changes in recent decades is the integration of digital literacy into language learning. Digital literacy refers to the ability to effectively find, evaluate, create, and communicate information using digital technologies. In language education, it enables both teachers and learners to use various online tools and resources to enhance communication and language acquisition.

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XALQ PEDAGOGIKASINING ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDAGI TALQINI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xalq pedagogikasining zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati, uning tarbiyaviy va ma'naviy funksiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Xalq og'zaki ijodi, urf-odatlar, qadriyatlar va milliy pedagogik tajribalar asosida shakllangan ta'limiy g'oyalar bugungi kunda yosh avlodni ma'naviy barkamol, milliy o'zlikni anglagan, ijtimoiy faol shaxs sifatida tarbiyalashda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqotda xalq pedagogikasini ta'lim dasturlariga integratsiya qilishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari, raqamli ta'lim muhitida folklor resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari hamda pedagogik tajribalar o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xalq pedagogikasi, xalq og'zaki ijodi, zamonaviy ta'lim, milliy qadriyatlar, ma'naviy tarbiya, raqamli ta'lim, integratsiya

Abstract: This article examines the significance of folk pedagogy in contemporary education and analyzes its moral, cultural, and educational functions. The educational concepts formed on the basis of folk oral traditions, customs, and national values play an essential role in developing spiritually mature, socially active individuals with strong national identity. The study explores modern approaches to integrating folk pedagogy into educational curricula, the application of folklore resources in digital learning environments, and relevant pedagogical practices.

Keywords: folk pedagogy, oral folklore, modern education, national values, moral upbringing, digital learning, integration

“Xalq donishmandligi – eng buyuk maktabdir” O'zbek xalq maqoli

Bugungi globallashuv jarayonida milliy ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan eng muhim vazifalardan biri – yosh avlodni nafaqat zamonaviy bilimlar bilan qurollantirish, balki ularning ma'naviy-axloqiy dunyosini boyitish, milliy o'zlik va qadriyatlarga hurmat ruhida tarbiyalashdir. Bu jarayonning muvaffaqiyati esa asrlar davomida shakllangan xalq donishmandligi, tarbiyaviy tajribalari va ma'naviy merosidan oqilona foydalanishni talab etadi. Xalq pedagogikasi - millat madaniy xotirasining eng qadimiy qatlamlarini o'z ichiga olgan, hayotiy tajriba va axloqiy mezonlarga asoslangan tarbiyaviy tizim bo'lib, u orqali jamiyatning ma'naviy poydevori, urf-odatlar, e'tiqodlari va ijtimoiy qadriyatlari avlodlardan-avlodga yetkazib kelingan. Xalq pedagogikasining tarbiyaviy imkoniyatlari deganda xalq tarbiya tajribasidan joy olgan eng ilg'or pedagogik bilimlar, malaka va ko'nikmalar, zamonaviy o'quv dargohi va oila tarbiyaviy tizimida yoshlarni tarbiyalash maqsad va vazifalarini hal etish uchun qulay shart- sharoitlarni yaratish tushuniladi [1].

Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida xalq pedagogikasining ahamiyati yangicha mazmun kasb etmoqda. Zero, xalq og'zaki ijodi, an'anaviy udumlar, tarixiy-falsafiy qarashlar hamda milliy tarbiya tamoyillari o'quvchilarda ma'naviy barkamollikni shakllantirishda, ijtimoiy faollik va fuqarolik pozitsiyasini rivojlantirishda, milliy madaniyatga hurmat tuyg'usini kuchaytirishda beqiyos pedagogik imkoniyatga ega. Xalq pedagogikasining ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilinishi o'quvchilarning o'zlikni anglashini chuqurlashtiradi, milliy identitetning mustahkamlanishiga xizmat qiladi va zamonaviy raqamli ta'lim muhitida ham samarali qo'llanishi mumkin bo'lgan tarbiyaviy modelni shakllantiradi.

Xalq pedagogikasi bugungi ta'lim tizimida yoshlarni milliy qadriyatlarga sodiq, ma'naviy barkamol, ijtimoiy faollikka ega shaxslar etib tarbiyalashda muhim manba sifatida namoyon bo'lishi asoslab berilgan [2]. Shu nuqtai nazardan, xalq pedagogikasini nafaqat tarixiy manba sifatida o'rganish, balki uni zamonaviy didaktik texnologiyalar, raqamli ta'lim vositalari, innovatsion metodlar bilan uyg'unlashtirish dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy vazifa

hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot davomida xalq pedagogikasining tarbiyaviy imkoniyatlari, ularning zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonidagi tatbiqi hamda yosh avlodni barkamol shaxs sifatida kamol toptirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi.

Xalq pedagogikasining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari ko'plab tarixiy va zamonaviy tadqiqotlarda chuqur o'rganilgan. Pedagogik merosni ilmiy tahlil qilish jarayonida Abu Nasr Forobiy [3], Ibn Sino [4], Alisher Navoiy [5], Ahmad Yassaviy [6] kabi allomalarning asarlarida ta'lim-tarbiya mazmuni, inson komilligi, axloqiy tarbiya tamoyillari asosiy ustuvor yo'nalish sifatida talqin etilgan. Ularning g'oyalari xalq og'zaki ijodi, urf-odatlar va ma'naviy qadriyatlarga tayangan holda shakllangan bo'lib, yosh avlodni bilimli, odobli va ma'naviy pok tarbiyalashni ko'zlagan.

Mustaqillik yillarida xalq pedagogikasining ilmiy ahamiyati yanada oshdi. O'zbekistonlik olimlar - A. Avliyoqulov [7], N. Azizxo'jayeva [8], J. Hasanboyeva, Q. Shodiyev, S. Jalolov, M. Ochilovlarning tadqiqotlarida xalq tarbiyaviy tajribalari zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi bilan uyg'un holda tahlil qilib borilgan. Ular milliy tarbiya konsepsiyasi, shaxsni har tomonlama rivojlantirish, ma'naviy qadriyatlarni saqlash va uzviy ravishda ta'lim jarayoniga tatbiq etish g'oyalarini asoslab bergan.

“Yana bir boshqa ma'lumotlarga qaraganda, “Globalashuv davrida yoshlarni ta'limva tarbiyalash samaradorligini oshirishda xalq pedagogikasining o'rni” mavzusining maqsad va vazifalari: Maqsad:1. Ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish asosiy maqsad –globalashuv sharoitida xalq pedagogikasini joriy etish orqali yoshlarga ta'lim va tarbiya sifatini oshirish.

Ushbu ilmiy manbalar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, xalq pedagogik merosi zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida shaxsning ma'naviy-axloqiy kamolotini ta'minlashda kuchli manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi va innovatsion ta'lim yondashuvlari bilan uyg'un qo'llanishi mumkin.

Metodolgiya. Tadqiqot davomida quyidagi ilmiy metodlardan foydalanildi: Tarixiy-pedagogik tahlil - xalq tarbiyasi merosining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi o'rganildi. Komparativ tahlil - xalq pedagogikasining zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi bilan uyg'unlashuv jihatlari solishtirildi. Kontent-analiz - ilmiy adabiyotlar va tarixiy manbalar tahlil qilindi. Pedagogik kuzatuv - xalq og'zaki ijodi asosida ta'lim jarayonidagi natijalar baholandi va natijalar qismida jadval asosida xalq pedagogikasining zamonaviy ta'limdagi o'rni talqin etildi. Xalq pedagogikasining tarixiy bosqichlari:

Xalq pedagogikasining rivojlanishi bir necha bosqichda kechgan:

Qadimgi davr (mil.avv. IX –milodiy VIII asrlar):mehnat, urf-odat, marosimlar orqali tarbiya berish davri.

O'rta asrlar davri:islom, ilm, axloq va ma'rifat asosida shakllangan tarbiya tizimi.

XIX asr –jadidchilik davri:milliy uyg'onish, ma'rifat va maktab islohotlari orqali xalq tarbiyasi yangi mazmun kasb etgan.

XX–XXI asrlar:mustaqillik davrida xalq pedagogikasi milliy ta'lim siyosatining tarkibiy qismiga aylandi.

Har bir bosqichdaxalq pedagogikasining mazmuni jamiyat ehtiyojlariga mos ravishda boyib bordi [10].

Xalq pedagogikasi qadriyatlari zamonaviy ta'limdagi shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvga asos bo'ladi. Raqamli o'quv muhitida xalq ijodiy merosidan foydalanish o'quvchining ma'naviy immunitetini mustahkamlaydi. Oila va mahalla institutlarini ta'lim jarayoniga jalb qilish yoshlarning ijtimoiy faol va axloqiy barkamol bo'lishiga xizmat qiladi.

Xalq pedagogikasining zamonaviy ta'limdagi talqini 1-Jadval

№	Yo'nalish	Zamonaviy talqini	Ta'lim jarayonidagi ifodasi
1	Insonparvarlik va axloqiy qadriyatlar	Milliy va umuminsoniy fazilatlarni rivojlantirish	O'quvchi shaxsini hurmat qilish, odob-axloq darslari, ijtimoiy-

			emotsional kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish
2	Oila va jamoa tarbiyasi	Ta'limda oila–maktab–mahalla hamkorligini kuchaytirish	Ota-ona bilan hamkorlik, tarbiyaviy tadbirlar, mahalla ishtiroki
3	Milliy o'zlik va vatanparvarlik	Milliy identitet va fuqarolik madaniyatini mustahkamlash	Tarixiy merosni o'rganish, davlat ramzlarini hurmat qilish, vatanparvarlik loyihalari
4	Xalq og'zaki ijodi orqali tarbiya	Ma'naviy-estetik tarbiya, badiiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish	Ertak, maqol-matal, doston va xalq qo'shiqlaridan ta'limda foydalanish
5	Qadriyat va an'analarni davom ettirish	Tarbiya jarayonida uzviylik va merosiylik	O'zbek milliy urf-odatlarini dars va tadbirlarda qo'llash
6	Amaliy hayotga tayyorlash	Hayotiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish	Mehnat tarbiyasi, hunar o'rgatish, hamkorlikda ishlash, ijtimoiy tajriba
7	Ma'naviy-ruhiy sog'lomlik	Psixologik madaniyatni rivojlantirish	Xulq-odob, sabr-toqat, o'zini boshqarish, hurmat-ehtirom

Xalq pedagogikasi - milliy tarbiyaning asosi bo'lib, u yosh avlodda vatanparvarlik, ma'naviy poklik, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat va komil inson fazilatlarini shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy ta'limda xalq pedagogikasi metodlarini interfaol texnologiyalar, raqamli ta'lim vositalari va kompetensiyaviy yondashuvlar bilan uyg'un qo'llash ta'lim samaradorligini oshiradi. Shuningdek, xalq pedagogikasi g'oyalarini ta'lim standartlari, darslik va metodikalar mazmuniga chuqur tatbiq etish bugungi kunning dolzarb vazifasidir.

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MA'LUMOTLARNI TIZIMLI TAHLIL QILISHNING PEDAGOGIK ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI

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Abstract: This article examines the systematic analysis of information within educational and informational systems. The study highlights the importance of structured data collection, interpretation, and feedback in effective decision-making processes. Drawing on the research of Uzbek and international scholars, the article argues that systematic information

analysis ensures higher educational quality, institutional adaptability, and technology-based learning improvements. The paper concludes by recommending practical strategies for integrating systematic information analysis into higher education and teacher development programs.

Keywords: systematic information analysis; data-based pedagogy; digital education; educational management; information systems.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'limiy va axborot tizimlari doirasida axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish masalasi o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda samarali qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarida tuzilgan ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, talqin etish va fikr-mulohazalarni qayta aloqa shaklida qaytarishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. O'zbekistonlik va xalqaro olimlarning ilmiy izlanishlariga tayangan holda, maqolada axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish ta'lim sifatini oshirishi, muassasalarning moslashuvchanligini ta'minlashi hamda texnologiyaga asoslangan o'qitish jarayonlarini takomillashtirishga xizmat qilishi ta'kidlangan. Maqola oliy ta'lim va o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish dasturlariga axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilishni integratsiya etish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar bilan yakunlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish; ma'lumotlarga asoslangan pedagogika; raqamli ta'lim; ta'lim boshqaruvi; axborot tizimlari.

Raqamli axborot asrida ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va ulardan oqilona foydalanish masalasi har bir sohada, xususan, ta'lim tizimida alohida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tizimli tahlil - bu ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, qayta ishlash, baholash va ular asosida qaror qabul qilish jarayonini puxta tashkil etish demakdir. Bu jarayonning muvaffaqiyati, avvalo, ma'lumotlarning to'liqligi, ishonchliligi va ularni tahlil qiluvchi subyektlarning tayyorgarligiga bog'liq.

O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida raqamli texnologiyalar joriy etilayotgan hozirgi davrda tizimli tahlil tamoyillari yanada muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Pedagogik faoliyatda o'qituvchi o'quvchi haqidagi ma'lumotlarni (uning o'zlashtirish darajasi, motivatsiyasi, ishtiroki) tizimli tahlil qilgan holda individual yondashuvni shakllantiradi. Bu esa shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'limni amalda qo'llashga imkon yaratadi.

Tizimli tahlil nafaqat ma'lumotlarni o'rganish, balki ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini aniqlash, sabab-natija munosabatlarini tushunish, shuningdek, o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi. Masalan, Sh. G'ulomov va T. Sattorov (2021) ta'kidlaganidek, axborot tizimlarining rivoji boshqaruv qarorlarini tez va aniq qabul qilishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shunday ekan, har bir pedagog o'z faoliyatida ma'lumotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishi zarur.

Zamonaviy ta'limda tizimli tahlil metodologiyasi o'quv dasturlari, baholash natijalari va talabalar faoliyatini chuqur tahlil qilish orqali sifatni oshirishga qaratilgan. Misol uchun, A. S. Qodirov (2020) "Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar" asarida aytganidek, ma'lumotlarni to'plash va ularni tahlil qilish, o'qituvchiga o'quv jarayonini boshqarishda yangi imkoniyatlar beradi. Shu bois, oliy ta'lim muassasalari axborot tizimlari asosida o'qitish sifatini monitoring qilish, natijalarni prognozlash va xulosalar chiqarish bo'yicha maxsus tahliliy modellarni joriy etmoqda.

Tizimli tahlilning amaliy bosqichlari quyidagicha kechadi: ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, ularni tasniflash, statistik va sifat tahlilini o'tkazish, hamda yakuniy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Mazkur jarayonni avtomatlashtirish uchun "Axborot boshqaruv tizimlari", "Elektron jurnal", "EduAction", "MyStat" kabi platformalar O'zbekiston ta'lim muassasalarida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Bular o'quv jarayonini raqamli ma'lumotlar asosida baholashga imkon yaratadi.

Ammo tizimli tahlilni samarali amalga oshirishda muammolar ham mavjud. Ulardan eng muhimi - kadrlar malakasi, ma'lumotlarni to'plash va ularni tahlil qilish bo'yicha metodik ko'nikmalarning yetishmasligi. Shuningdek, ayrim hollarda ma'lumotlarning ishonchligi past bo'lishi natijasida tahlil xulosalari ham noto'g'ri shakllanishi mumkin. Shu sababli pedagogik tizimda tahlil madaniyatini shakllantirish, o'qituvchilarni statistik tahlil usullariga o'rgatish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tizimli tahlilning asosiy afzalligi - qarorlar qabul qilishda obyektivlikni ta'minlashidir. Har bir qaror empirik ma'lumotlarga asoslanadi, bu esa subyektiv fikrning ta'sirini kamaytiradi. Ma'lumotlarni tizimli o'rganish orqali ta'lim muassasalari samaradorligini oshirish, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va natijadorlikni oshirish mumkin. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi "Raqamli ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish to'g'risida"gi qarorida ham aynan ma'lumotlarni tahlil asosida boshqarish konsepsiyasi ilgari surilgan.

Shunday qilib, tizimli tahlil nafaqat texnik yoki informatika sohasi uchun, balki pedagogik amaliyot uchun ham dolzarb ilmiy yo'nalishdir. Ta'lim sohasida tizimli yondashuv o'quv jarayonining har bir bosqichini raqamli nazorat ostiga olib, o'quvchining individual rivojlanishini kuzatish imkonini beradi. Tahlil natijalari o'qituvchiga strategik qarorlar qabul qilishda, o'quvchi uchun esa o'z ustida ishlashda yo'l-yo'riq beradi. Shu bois, har bir oliy ta'lim muassasasi o'z ilmiy-tahliliy infratuzilmasini rivojlantirib borishi zarur.

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XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA KOUCH-TRENINGNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada tarbiya jarayonida kouching (kouch-trening) texnologiyalarini qo'llashning nazariy asoslari, maqsadlari, metodlari va amaliy natijalari tahlil qilinadi. Tarbiyachi va tarbiyalanuvchi o'rtasida samarali muloqot, ishonch, shaxsiy o'sish va hayotiy maqsadlarga erishishga xizmat qiluvchi kouchlik usullari ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarbiya, kouch-trening, metodlar, tarbiyachi, tarbiyalanuvchi, shaxsiy rivojlanish, muloqot qobiliyati, ishonch, muloqot.

Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations, goals, methods and practical results of using coaching (coach-training) technologies in the educational process. Coaching methods that serve to promote effective communication, trust, personal growth and achievement of life goals between the educator and the student are revealed.

Keywords: education, coach-training, methods, educator, student, personal development, communication skills, trust, communication.

Bugungi kunda ta'lim va tarbiya sohasida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlar ustuvor ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Faqatgina ta'lim berish emas, balki yoshlarning shaxsiy rivojlanishi,

tanqidiy fikrlashi, o'zini anglashi va hayotiy maqsadlarni belgilashida yordam berish - bugungi tarbiyaning asosiy vazifalaridan biridir. Shu nuqtai nazardan, kouching texnologiyasi tarbiya sohasida yangi va samarali vosita sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Kouch-trening - bu zamonaviy tarbiya tizimida muhim o'rin egallayotgan yangi yondashuvdir. U nafaqat yosh avlodning bilim olishi, balki ularning shaxsiy rivojlanishi, hayotiy maqsadlarini belgilashi va ijtimoiy ongini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Tarbiyachilar, psixologlar va pedagoglar ushbu yondashuvni o'z amaliyotiga joriy etish orqali tarbiya samaradorligini keskin oshirishlari mumkin.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida xorijiy tillarni bilish shaxsiy va kasbiy rivojlanishning muhim omiliga aylandi. Shu bois ta'limda faqat grammatika va leksikani o'rgatish emas, balki talabalarni shaxs sifatida rivojlantirish, ularda ishonch, motivatsiya va muloqot qobiliyatini shakllantirish muhim vazifalardan biridir. Bu jarayonda kouch-trening texnologiyasi o'zining samaradorligi bilan ajralib turibdi.

Kouching (inglizcha "coaching") - bu shaxsiy rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan, savol-javob va mulohazaga asoslangan faol tarbiyaviy jarayondir. Kouch-trener - bu o'qituvchi emas, balki yo'l boshlovchi, rag'batlantiruvchi va shaxsiy o'sishga sharoit yaratuvchi mutaxassisdir. U tarbiyalanuvchidagi ichki salohiyatni ochishga yordam beradi

Kouching - bu o'qituvchi va o'rganuvchi o'rtasidagi hamkorlikka asoslangan faol muloqot jarayoni bo'lib, shaxsiy rivojlanish, maqsad belgilash, qaror qabul qilish va o'z potentsialini ochishga qaratilgan. Kouch-treningda o'qituvchi o'zini "bilim manbai" emas, balki yo'naltiruvchi, rag'batlantiruvchi va tinglovchi sifatida namoyon etadi.

Tarbiyada kouch-treningning asosiy maqsadlari: Shaxsiy mas'uliyat hissini shakllantirish; Yoshlarda maqsad qo'yish va unga erishish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish; Muammoli vaziyatlarni hal etish qobiliyatini shakllantirish; Ishonch, muloqot va hamkorlik muhitini yaratish; O'zini anglash va refleksiyaning rag'batlantirish.

Kouch-trening usullari va amaliyotlari: 1. Savol-berish texnikasi (Powerful Questioning)

Tarbiyachi savol berish orqali bolani fikrlashga undaydi, muammoni o'zboshimchalik bilan hal qilishni emas, balki tahlil qilish va echimni topishga yo'naltiradi.

2. Refleksiya mashqlari (Self-reflection tasks) Talabalar yoki o'quvchilar o'zida kechayotgan his-tuyg'ular, tajribalar va fikrlarni yozma va og'zaki shaklda tahlil qiladi. O'zini anglashni kuchaytirish.

3. Hayotiy maqsadlar kartasi (Life goals mapping) Tarbiyalanuvchi o'z hayotidagi maqsadlarni yozadi, ularni muddatlar bo'yicha belgilaydi va amaliyotga tadbiiq qilish yo'llarini muhokama qiladi.

4. Feedback (Qayta aloqa) Fikr bildirishning samarali usuli sifatida, tarbiyachi va tarbiyalanuvchi o'zaro ochiq muloqotda bo'ladi. Tanqid emas, rag'bat, konstruktiv takliflar berish.

5. Visualization (Tasavvur orqali mashqlar) Yoshlar kelajakdagi o'z obrazini ko'z oldiga keltirib, bugungi kundan boshlab unga erishish qadamlarini belgilaydi.

Kouching va an'anaviy tarbiya

An'anaviy tarbiya	Kouch-trening
O'qituvchi markazda	Tarbiyalanuvchi markazda
Ta'lim berish	Savol berish va tahlil qilish
Nazorat	Hamkorlik
Tayyor echimlar	Mustaqil qaror qabul qilishga yordam
Baxolash	Refleksiya va fikr almashish

Kouch-treningning tarbiyadagi afzalliklari: Ijobiy psixologik muhit yaratiladi, Shaxsiy o‘shish va salohiyatni ochishga yordam beradi, Yoshlarda ishonch va mas’uliyat hissi shakllanadi, Faol muloqot va empatiya rivojlanadi, Tarbiya jarayonida demokratik munosabat paydo bo‘ladi

Xorijiy tilni o‘rganishda kouch-treningning afzalliklari

1. Ichki motivatsiyani shakllantiradi: Kouching savollari talabani o‘z maqsadlarini anglashga undaydi: “Sen nima uchun bu tilni o‘rganmoqchisan?”, “Bu senga qanday foyda beradi?”. Bunday yondashuv til o‘rganishga ixtiyoriy va mazmunli yondashuvni shakllantiradi.
2. Faol muloqot muhitini yaratadi: Kouch-trening jarayonida talabalar faqat tinglovchi emas, balki fikr bildiruvchi, savol beruvchi, bahslashuvchi faol ishtirokchilarga aylanadi. Bu esa tilda erkin so‘zlashishni rag‘batlantiradi.
3. O‘z-o‘zini baholash va refleksiyaning rivojlanishini ta’minlaydi: Kouchning asosiy vazifalaridan biri - talabani o‘z o‘rganish jarayonini kuzatish va tahlil qilishga o‘rgatishdir. “Sen nimaga erishding?”, “Qanday qiyinchiliklarga duch kelding?” kabi savollar talabani o‘ziga baho berishga undaydi.
4. Mas’uliyat va mustaqillikni oshiradi: Talaba o‘z o‘rganish jarayoni uchun mas’uliyatni his qiladi. Kouchning vazifasi - uni yo‘naltirish, ammo barcha qarorlarni talaba o‘zi qabul qiladi.
5. Emotsional qo‘llab-quvvatlashni ta’minlaydi: Kouch treningdagi muhit ishonchli, ijobiy va qo‘llovchi bo‘lib, talabalarda “men qila olaman” degan ishonchni shakllantiradi.

Amaliyotda qo‘llaniladigan kouch-trening usullari

Xulosa qilib aytganda, kouch-trening texnologiyasi xorijiy tillarni o‘rgatishda an’anaviy usullarga qo‘shimcha ravishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi. U talabalarning shaxsiy salohiyatini ochish, ishonchini oshirish, maqsadli va faol o‘rganish muhitini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy o‘qituvchi faqatgina ma’lumot beruvchi emas, balki talaba salohiyatini kashf etuvchi kouchga aylanishi lozim.

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KOUCHING YONDOSHUVLAR ASOSIDA INGLIZ TILI DARSLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL QILISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kouching yondoshuvlar asosida ingliz tili darslarini samarali tashkil qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari hamda zamonaviy ta’lim paradigmasi o‘quvchini shunchaki bilimni passiv qabul qiluvchi ob’ektdan o‘z ta’lim jarayonining faol ishtirokchisiga aylantirishga qaratilgan bo‘lib, ingliz tilini o‘rgatish jarayonida kouching yondashuvidan

foydalanish o'quvchilarning nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini samarali egallashiga, balki o'z-o'zini boshqarish, tanqidiy fikrlash va maqsadga intilish kabi muhim hayotiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishiga zamin yaratishi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kouching, texnologiya, real ta'lim, innovatsion, zamonaviy, tizim, intensivlashuv, metod, intellectual.

Annotation: In this article, the specifics of the effective organization of English lessons on the basis of coaching approaches, as well as the modern educational paradigm, are aimed at making the student simply a passive recipient of knowledge from an object to an active participant in his educational process, and the use of the coaching approach in the process of teaching English allows students not only to, it is thought that it provides the basis for the formation of important life competencies, such as critical thinking and striving for a goal.

Keywords: coaching, technology, real education, innovative, modern, system, intensification, method, intellectual.

Respublikamizda olib borilayotgan ta'lim jarayoniga oid siyosatlariga qo'yilgan yuksak talablar o'qituvchi faoliyatini yanada chuqurroq o'rganish bilan birga, uning o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-pedagogik jihatlarini tadqiq qilish bugungi zamonning talabi darajasiga aylanib bormoqda. Buning natijasi o'laroq, o'qitish tizimidagi innovatsiyalar, yangi texnologiyalar, metod va amiliy ishlar natijalari talabalarning motivatsion ta'limlarini rivojlantirish dolzarb masala ekanini ko'rsatmoqda.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 19-maydagi PQ-5117-son «O'zbekiston Respublikasida xorijiy tillarni o'rganishni ommalashtirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish choratadbirlari to'g'risida»gi qarorlari, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 11-avgustdagi 610-son «Ta'lim muassasalarida chet tillarini o'qitishning sifatini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida», 2019-yil 19-iyuldagi 606-son «Oliy malakali ilmiy va ilmiy pedagog kadrlarni maqsadli tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish to'g'risida» qarorlari bugungi kun xorijiy tillar yo'nalishini bitirayotgan kadrlarga nisbatda yuqori talablarni qo'ymoqda.

Kouching texnologiyalarining ta'lim amaliyotiga joriy etilishi zamonaviy pedagoglar uchun sifat jihatidan yangi chaqiriq hisoblanadi. Bu innovatsion texnologiya hali yetarlicha o'rganilmagan va real ta'lim sharoitlariga to'liq moslashtirilmagan bo'lsa-da, hozirgi davrda uning ahamiyati juda dolzarb ekanligi ta'kidlanishi lozim. Shu bilan birga, ta'lim jarayoniga kouchingni joriy etish muammosi ikki tomonlama xarakterga ega: bir tomondan, u o'qituvchilarning shaxsiy va kasbiy rivojlanishini talab qiladi, ikkinchi tomondan esa, ta'lim oluvchilarning o'quv jarayonidagi yangi metodlarni to'g'ri qabul qilishini ta'minlashi zarur. Ta'lim jarayonining intensivlashuvi doirasida har bir ishtirokchining intellektual salohiyatidan samarali foydalanish orqali ijobiy natijalarga erishish mumkin. Bu borada ingliz tili darslarida juda ko'p ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Ayniqsa, ingliz tili darslarini kouching yondoshuvlar asosida tashkil qilishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Bunda an'anaviy o'qitish metodlaridan farqli ravishda, o'quvchini dars jarayonining markaziga qo'ygan holda, uning shaxsiy ehtiyojlari, qobiliyatlari va maqsadlariga muvofiq ta'lim berishga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvdir.

Bu yondashuv motivatsiyani oshirish, mustaqillikni rivojlantirish va ingliz tilini faol va samarali o'rganish uchun qulay muhit yaratadi. Koyching yondoshuvlar asosida chet tili darslarini loyihalashtirishda quyidagilarga alohida etibor qaratish lozim:

Shaxsiy maqsadlarga asoslangan o'rganish

Kouching texnologiyasida har bir o'quvchining individual maqsadlari (masalan, IELTS ball olish, chet elda o'qish, kasbiy maqsadlar) aniqlanadi va darslar shu maqsadlarga mos ravishda yo'naltiriladi.

O'quvchining faol ishtirokini ta'minlash: Darslar markazida o'qituvchi emas, o'quvchi turadi. Kouchingda o'qituvchi yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatuvchi, motivatsiya beruvchi va sherik sifatida harakat qiladi. O'quvchi mustaqil ravishda maqsad qo'yadi, qaror qabul qiladi va o'z rivojlanishini baholaydi.

Refleksiya va o'zini baholash: Har bir darsdan so'ng o'quvchi o'zini baholash, nimani o'rganganini va qaerda qiyinlashayotganini tahlil qilish imkoniga ega bo'ladi. Bu jarayon o'quvchining o'z ustidan ishlash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi.

Motivatsiyani oshirish usullari: Kouching jarayonida o'quvchining ichki motivatsiyasiga e'tibor qaratiladi. Uning qo'ruqlari, shubhalari va ishonchsizligi bilan ishlash, pozitiv fikrlashni shakllantirish – muhim vazifalardan biri.

Faol ta'lim metodlari bilan uyg'unlashtirish: Kouching texnologiyasi debate, role-play, case-study, problem-solving, project-based learning kabi zamonaviy metodlar bilan birga qo'llaniladi. Bu darslarni jonli va ta'sirli qiladi.

Kouching yondoshuvlar asosida chet tili darslarini loyihalashtirish natijasida: o'quvchining til o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishi ortadi, maqsadli va natijaga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim ta'minlanadi, o'quvchilarda kritik fikrlash, mustaqil qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalari shakllanadi, darslarda ijobiy psixologik muhit yaratiladi.

Tadqiqotlarimiz jarayonida ingliz tili darslarini kouching texnologiyalari asosida samarali tashkil etish uchun quyidagi usullar va yondashuvlardan foydalandik. Ular ta'lim jarayonini individuallashtirish, o'quvchining motivatsiyasini oshirish va o'z ustidan ishlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilad.

Ingliz tili darslarida kouching yondashuvining o'ziga xosligini anglash uchun uni an'anaviy o'qitishdan farqlovchi jihatlarini ko'rib chiqish lozim. An'anaviy darsda o'qituvchi asosiy bilim manbai bo'lsa, kouchingda o'qituvchi (kouch) o'quvchining (kouchi) o'z yechimlarini topishga yordam beruvchi yo'naltiruvchi (fasilitator) vazifasini bajaradi.

Kouching texnologiyalarini ingliz tili darslariga integratsiya qilish o'quv jarayonini tubdan o'zgartiradi va bir qator o'ziga xos xususiyatlar bilan ajralib turadi:

1. O'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan va shaxsiylashtirilgan yondashuv. Kouching yondashuvi har bir o'quvchining individual ehtiyojlari, qiziqishlari va o'rganish uslublarini birinchi o'ringa qo'yadi. Darslar qat'iy belgilangan darslik doirasidan chiqib, o'quvchining real hayotiy maqsadlariga (masalan, chet elda o'qish, xalqaro anjumanda ma'ruza qilish, sevimli filmini original tilda tushunish) moslashtiriladi. Bu esa o'quvchining ichki motivatsiyasini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

2. Maqsadlarni aniq belgilash va unga erishish strategiyasini ishlab chiqish. Dars jarayoni o'quvchi bilan hamkorlikda aniq, o'lchanadigan, erishib bo'ladigan, dolzarb va vaqt bilan cheklangan (SMART) maqsadlar qo'yishdan boshlanadi. O'qituvchi-kouch o'quvchiga "Nima uchun ingliz tilini o'rganmoqchisan?", "Qanday natijaga erishmoqchisan?", "Bunga qanday yo'l bilan erishish mumkin?" kabi ochiq savollar berish orqali uning o'z maqsadini anglashiga va unga olib boruvchi shaxsiy rejasini tuzishiga yordam beradi.

3. Kuchli savollar texnikasidan foydalanish. Kouchingning asosiy instrumenti – bu kuchli, ochiq va fikrlashga undovchi savollardir. O'qituvchi tayyor javoblarni berish o'rniga, "Bu vaziyatda yana qanday yo'l tutish mumkin?", "Bu xatodan qanday saboq olding?", "Qaysi usul senga ko'proq samara beryapti?" kabi savollar orqali o'quvchini mustaqil izlanishga, tahlil qilishga va o'z yechimlarini topishga yo'naltiradi. Bu o'quvchida tanqidiy fikrlash va muammolarni hal qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.

4. O'z-o'zini anglash va o'rganish uchun mas'uliyatni oshirish. Kouching yondashuvi o'quvchini o'z o'rganish jarayonining egasi bo'lishga undaydi. O'quvchilar o'z yutuqlari va qiyinchiliklarini o'zlari tahlil qilishni, samarali o'rganish strategiyalarini tanlashni va o'z

rivojlanishlari uchun mas'uliyatni his qilishni o'rganadilar. Bu ularning o'quv mustaqilligini (learner autonomy) shakllantiradi.

5. Qo'llab-quvvatlovchi va ishonchga asoslangan muhit yaratish. Samarali kouching uchun o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasida ishonchli hamkorlik munosabatlari o'rnatilishi shart. O'quvchi xato qilishdan qo'rqmaydigan, o'z fikrini erkin ayta oladigan va har doim qo'llab-quvvatlashni his qiladigan xavfsiz muhitda o'z salohiyatini to'liq namoyon eta oladi. O'qituvchi-kouchning vazifasi nafaqat til o'rgatish, balki o'quvchining o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini mustahkamlashdir.

6. Interaktiv va amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan metodlardan foydalanish. Kouching asosidagi darslar an'anaviy ma'ruzalardan ko'ra ko'proq interaktiv mashg'ulotlarga tayanadi. Rolli o'yinlar, real hayotiy vaziyatlar simulyatsiyasi, loyiha ishlari, munozaralar kabi metodlar o'quvchilarning o'rgangan bilimlarini darhol amaliyotda qo'llashlariga va muloqot ko'nikmalarini faol rivojlantirishlariga imkon beradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, kouching texnologiyalari asosida ingliz tili darslarini tashkil qilish: individual shaxsga yo'naltirilgan va maqsadga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvni ta'minlaydi, motivatsiya va rivojlanishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, talabani faol, mustaqil va ishonchli shaxsga aylantiradi.

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СТРЕСС В ЛИДЕРСТВЕ И ЕГО ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются ключевые аспекты стресса и его психологические характеристики в деятельности руководителей. Приведены мнения ведущих психологов мира о путях устранения стресса в организационном управлении, а также подробно освещены вопросы профилактики и управления стрессом. Отмечается, что стресс является неотъемлемой частью управленческой деятельности, а умение эффективно справляться с ним – важный компонент профессиональной компетенции лидера.

Ключевые слова: стресс, управление, сопротивление, мобилизация, эмоциональный, психологический тренинг, психология.

В современном обществе проблема стресса рассматривается как одно из наиболее актуальных направлений психологических исследований. Эмоциональное напряжение невозможно полностью устранить или избежать, однако важно научиться взаимодействовать со стрессовыми факторами конструктивно. Исследования Н.Н. Бехтеревой (1974), Ф.Е. Василюка (1999), М.В. Коркиной (1998), Л.А. Китаева-Смыка (1983) показывают, что стрессовые состояния могут проявляться по-разному на различных этапах жизни человека, что связано с особенностями нервной и гормональной систем.

Современные определения понятия «стресс» включают следующие формулировки: - стресс - это особое состояние психики и организма, характеризующееся мобилизацией функциональных резервов для преодоления экстремальных воздействий;- стресс - тревожное состояние, которое организм стремится преодолеть или снизить;- стресс - психологическая и моральная реакция, отражающая внутреннее беспокойство или его подавление.

В психологии стресс определяется как неспецифическая реакция организма на предъявляемые требования внешней или внутренней среды. Термин «стресс» (от англ. stress - «напряжение, давление») активно используется в физиологии, психологии и медицине. Проблема стресса впервые была выделена в научных исследованиях Г. Селье, который описал три фазы его протекания: реакция тревоги, стадия сопротивления и стадия истощения. На первой стадии организм активизирует все ресурсы, на второй - адаптируется к стрессору, а на третьей - истощает свои запасы, что может привести к психосоматическим расстройствам.

Причинами стресса могут быть как внешние, так и внутренние факторы. К внешним относятся профессиональные трудности, изменение условий работы, конфликты, потери близких и т.д. К внутренним - личные ценности, убеждения, самооценка и субъективное восприятие ситуации. В стрессовом состоянии человек может испытывать раздражительность, апатию, недоверие к окружающим, что отражается на его поведении и профессиональной эффективности.

Методы исследования

Объектом исследования выступил образовательный процесс студентов. При изучении темы использовались педагогические и теоретические методы – наблюдения и анализ, дополненные описанием индивидуальных психологических особенностей.

Если устранение стрессогенных факторов затягивается, начинается третья стадия – истощение. Организм теряет способность к адаптации и расходует невозможные резервы, что повышает риск возникновения заболеваний. В.А. Бодров классифицирует стресс по типам: физиологический, психоэмоциональный, коммуникативный и информационный. Психоэмоциональный стресс связан с сильными переживаниями – гневом, страхом, чувством вины, тревогой и др.

Подводя итоги, можно отметить, что стрессоустойчивость и стрессовая выносливость не являются полностью тождественными понятиями. Стрессоустойчивость предполагает не только способность переносить стрессовую ситуацию, но и сохранять физическое и психическое здоровье, эффективно решая возникающие задачи. Умение управлять стрессом играет ключевую роль в профессиональной деятельности руководителя, повышая его эффективность и стабильность коллектива.

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FASILITATOR YONDASHUVI ASOSIDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O‘QITISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy ta’limda muhim o‘rin tutayotgan fasilitator (yoki yordamchi, yo‘naltiruvchi) yondoshuvi haqida fikr yuritiladi. Xususan, xorijiy tillarni o‘qitish jarayonida fasilitatorning roli, usullari va natijadorligi tahlil etiladi. Shu bilan birga, an’anaviy o‘qituvchi modelidan farqli ravishda, talabani faol ishtirokchiga aylantiruvchi faol ta’lim muhitini yaratishga e’tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: xorijiy tillar, fasilitator, an’anaviy, model, yaratish, to‘ldirish, shaxsiy va kasbiy, metodik yondashuvlar, interaktiv.

Abstract: This article discusses the facilitator (or assistant, guide) approach, which plays an important role in modern education. In particular, the role, methods and effectiveness of the facilitator in the process of teaching foreign languages are analyzed. At the same time, unlike the traditional teacher model, attention is paid to creating an active learning environment that turns the student into an active participant.

Keywords: foreign languages, facilitator, traditional, model, creation, complementation, personal and professional, methodological approaches, interactive.

Bugungi kunda ta’lim sohasidagi global o‘zgarishlar fonida o‘qituvchidan talabalarni bilim bilan "to‘ldirish" emas, balki ularning faol ishtirokini rag‘batlantirish, mustaqil izlanishga undash kabi vazifalarni bajarish talab etilmoqda. Bu jarayonda o‘qituvchi fasilitator, ya’ni yo‘naltiruvchi, ko‘makchi sifatida faoliyat olib boradi. Xususan, xorijiy tillarni o‘rgatish jarayonida bu yondashuv o‘ta samarali natijalarni bermoqda. Bugungi kunda globallashuv va axborot texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi natijasida xorijiy tillarni bilish nafaqat bilim darajasini, balki shaxsiy va kasbiy o‘sish imkoniyatlarini ham belgilaydi. Shu bois, til o‘rgatishdagi an’anaviy yondoshuvlardan zamonaviy, interaktiv va shaxsga yo‘naltirilgan metodlarga o‘tish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu metodlardan biri - fasilitatorlik yondoshuvidir.

Fasilitator - bu an’anaviy ma’noda darsni faqatgina tushuntiruvchi emas, balki talabalarni o‘ylashga, mulohaza qilishga, mustaqil izlanishga undaydigan shaxsdir. U dars jarayonida yo‘l-yo‘riq ko‘rsatadi, muhit yaratadi, faol muloqotni rag‘batlantiradi va talabaning shaxsiy o‘sishiga ko‘maklashadi.

Fasilitator-o‘qituvchining asosiy vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat: Qulay muhit yaratish: Talabalar o‘z fikrlarini erkin bayon eta oladigan, xato qilishdan qo‘rqmaydigan, o‘zaro hurmat va ishonchga asoslangan psixologik qulay muhitni yaratish.

Jarayonni boshqarish: Munozaralar, guruh ishlari va loyihalarni samarali tashkil etish, barcha talabalarining faol ishtirokini ta’minlash va jarayonni belgilangan maqsad sari yo‘naltirish.

Resurslar bilan ta’minlash: Talabalarga kerakli axborot manbalarini, o‘quv materiallarini tavsiya qilish va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo‘llarini o‘rgatish.

Refleksiyani rag‘batlantirish: Talabalarni o‘z o‘quv faoliyatini tahlil qilishga, yutuq va kamchiliklarini anglashga va kelgusi rivojlanish yo‘llarini belgilashga undash.

Xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishda fasilitatorning vazifalari: dars maqsadlarini birgalikda belgilash; interaktiv va ijodiy faoliyatlarni tashkil qilish; har bir talabaning ehtiyoj va qiziqishlarini hisobga olish; yaxshi til muhitini yaratish; muloqot markazida talabalarni qo'yish; talabalar o'rtasida hamkorlik muhitini shakllantirish.

Bunda talabalar faol ishtirok etadi; tilda erkin muloqotga kirishadi; ijodiy fikrlash rivojlanadi; jamoaviy ishlash ko'nikmalari shakllanadi; ta'lim sifati oshadi. Fasilitatorlik yondoshuvi xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishda yangi imkoniyatlar eshigini ochadi. Bu yondashuv talabalarning faolligini oshirib, ularni mustaqil o'rganuvchi va muloqotchi sifatida shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy dunyoda tilni nafaqat grammatik me'yorda, balki muloqot vositasi sifatida o'rgatishda fasilitatorning roli beqiyosdir.

Talabalarga: fasilitatorlik bo'yicha seminarlar tashkil etish;

darslarda interaktiv metodlar ulushini oshirish;

talabalarning shaxsiy o'rganish strategiyalarini rivojlantirish;

elektron resurslardan samarali foydalanish.

Fasilitator yondoshuvida samarali metodlar

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Fasilitator yondoshuvi xorijiy tillarni o'qitishni yanada jonli, amaliy va talabalar uchun qiziqarli jarayonga aylantiradi. U o'quvchilarni passiv tinglovchidan faol ishtirokchiga, bilimni iste'mol qiluvchidan uni mustaqil izlab topuvchi va yaratuvchi shaxsga aylantiradi. Kommunikativ, vazifaga va loyihaga asoslangan metodikalarni qo'llash orqali fasilitator-o'qituvchi nafaqat til bilish darajasini, balki talabalarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini, muloqot madaniyatini va mustaqil ta'lim olish ko'nikmalarini ham rivojlantiradi. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida raqobatbardosh mutaxassis bo'lishni istagan har bir xorijiy til o'qituvchisi fasilitatorlik kompetentsiyalarini egallashi shart.

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TARBIYA DARSLARIDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarbiya darslarida o'quvchilarida kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish, kitob mutolaa qilish odobi, kitobdan to'g'ri foydalanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda o'qish darslarining ahamiyati yoritib berilgan. Kitob avvalo ma'naviyat manbayi, hayotiy maktabdur. Farzandlarimizni qanchalik kitobxon qilib tarbiyalasak jamiyatimiz shunchalik rivojlanadi va ziyoli bo'ladi. Ma'naviyatni yuksaltirish, yoshlar o'rtasida kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish, kitob mutolaasi insonni ma'naviy kamolot sari yetaklashini, insonni har tomonlama yetuk, komil shaxs sifatida shakllanishidagi o'rni nihoyatda beqiyosdir. Jumladan, sharq mutafakkirlari qarashlarida, g'oyalarida,

asarlarida inson kamoloti, ma'naviy yetuklik, vatanparvarlik, ta'limtarbiya kabi masalalarda qimmatli ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ma'naviyat, yoshlar, madaniyat, kitob mutolaasi, komil shaxs, g'oyalar, mutolaa, kitobxonlik, ta'lim-tarbiya, mustaqil o'qish, sinfdan tashqari o'qish.

Annotation: this article highlights the importance of reading lessons in the formation of reading culture, the etiquette of reading, the skills of correct use of the book in the lessons of Education. The book is primarily a source of spirituality, a life School. The more readers we raise our children, the more our society develops and becomes intellectual. The role of raising spirituality, the formation of a culture of reading among young people, the reading of the book leads a person towards spiritual perfection, and the formation of a person as a mature, perfect person in every possible way is extremely incomparable. In particular, in the views, ideas, works of Eastern thinkers, valuable information was given on such issues as human perfection, spiritual maturity, patriotism, education. The role of raising spirituality, the formation of a culture of reading among young people, the reading of the book leads a person towards spiritual perfecting.

Keywords: spirituality, youth, culture, book reading, perfect personality, ideas, reading, reading, education, independent reading, extracurricular reading.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida yosh avlodning ma'naviy olamini boyitish, ularni milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalash har qachongidan ham muhimroq ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bu jarayonda "Tarbiya" fanining o'rni beqiyosdir. Tarbiya darslari o'quvchilarda axloqiy sifatlarni shakllantirish, ularni ijtimoiy mas'uliyatli, adolatli va halol insonlar etib tarbiyalashga qaratilgan. Ushbu maqsadlarga erishishning eng samarali vositalaridan biri esa shubhasiz, kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishdir. Zero, kitob inson tafakkurini o'stiruvchi, dunyoqarashini kengaytiruvchi va ma'naviy kamolotga yetaklovchi bebaho xazinadir. Inson tafakkurining o'sishi, bilim doirasining kengayishi, olam va voqealar haqidagi tasavvurlarining oshishi, insonning tinmay mutolaa qilishiga, o'z ustida tinmay izlanishiga bog'liq. Kitobxonlik madaniyatini yoshlikdan shakllantirib boorish lozim. Kitobning inson hayotidagi o'rni beqiyosdir.

Yoshlikdan bolada kitobga mehr tuyg'usini uyg'otish, bolaning ma'naviy oziqlanishiga, kamol topishiga yordam beradi. Ma'naviy barkamol, sog'lom fikrli Bolani kamol toptirishda boshlang'ich ta'limning o'rni kattadir. Bolada kitobga mehr uyg'otish, avvalo, oiladan boshlanadi. Ota-ona kitob mutolaa qilsa, farzandda ham asta-sekin kitob mutolaa qilish ko'nikmalari shakllanadi. Bolaga yoshlikdan qiziqarli ertaklar, hikoyalarni mutolaa qilib berish kerak. Maktabga endigina qadam qo'ygan bola kitobning qanchalik qimmatbaho boylik ekanligini anglab yetishi zarur. Bizning rivojlanib borayotgan mamlakatimizda ham kitobxonlikka katta e'tibor qaratilgan. Kitob, avvalo, hayotiy makyab, ma'naviyat manbaidir.

Yurtboshimiz tashabbuslari bilan mazkur masalalarga davlat siyosati darajasida qaralib, samarali ishlar yo'lga qo'yildi. Davlatimiz rahbari Sh.Mirziyoevning quyidagi fikrlarida ham yaqqol aks etgan: "Ayni paytda, axborotkommunikatsiya sohasidagi oxirgi yutuqlarni o'zlashtirish bilan 75 birga, yoshlarning kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirishga, ularni kitob bilan do'st bo'lishga, aholining kitobxonlik saviyasini yanada oshirishga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozim bo'ladi.

Buning uchun, avvalo, milliy adabiyotimiz va jahon adabiyotining eng sara namunalarini ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga joylashtirish va ularni keng targ'ib qilishga alohida e'tibor berishimiz muhim ahamiyat kasb yetadi". Prezidentning 2017 yil 12 yanvardagi "Kitob mahsulotlarini chop etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ibot qilish bo'yicha komissiya tuzish to'g'risida"gi F-4789-

sonli Farmoyishi bu borada keng ko'lamli islohotlarni amalga oshirishga zamin yaratdi. 2017-yil 13-sentyabrda "Kitob mahsulotlarini nashr etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ib qilish bo'yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar dasturi to'g'risidagi" PQ-3271-sonli qarorning qabul qilinishi va uning doirasida belgilangan vazifalar ham yurtimizda kitob mahsulotlarini chop etish, aholining kitobxonlik madaniyatini yuksaltirish borasida katta o'zgarishlarga zamin yaratdi.

Mamlakatimiz bo'ylab "Yosh kitobxon", "Eng faol kitobxon guruh", "Eng kitobxon oila" tanlovlarining tashkil qilinishi va g'olib kitobxonlar turli darajadagi qimmatbaho sovg'alar bilan taqdirlanishi, yirik nashriyotlar tomonidan o'zbek xalqi va jahon adabiyotining durdona asarlari qayta tahrirlanib, yanada sifatli nashr etilishi, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy ko'makka muhtoj fuqaro va oilalarga badiiy-estetik salmoqdor kitoblar, badiiy adabiyotlarning tuhfa qilinishi ushbu qonunlarda belgilangan vazifalar ijrosi bo'lishi bilan bir qatorda aholi, xususan, yosh avlodning mutolaa madaniyatini kamol toptirishga, ma'naviy-ma'rifiy tafakkurini yuksaltirishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratib bermoqda.

Mamlakatimizda keyingi yillarda yoshlar o'rtasida kitobxonlik madaniyatini targ'ib qilish borasidagi ishlar ko'lami sifat darajaga ko'tarildi. Xususan, O'zbekiston prezidentining 2017 yil 13 sentyabrdagi "Kitob mahsulotlarini nashr etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ib qilish bo'yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar dasturi to'g'risida"gi qarori, Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020 yil 14 dekabrda № 781-sonli qarori bilan 2020–2025 yillarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish va qo'llab-quvvatlash milliy dasturi va boshqa qator hujjatlar soha rivoji uchun dasturul amal vazifasini o'tamoqda.

Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020 yil 14 dekabrda № 781-sonli qarori bilan 2020–2025 yillarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish va qo'llab-quvvatlash milliy dasturini uch bosqichda amalga oshirish ko'zda tutilgan. I bosqich – 2020- 2021 yillarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish bo'yicha tashkiliy-huquqiy mexanizmlarni takomillash-tirish chora-tadbirlarini amalga oshirish; II bosqich – 2022-2023 yillarda kitobxonlikka oid infratuzilmani mustahkamlash; III bosqich – 2024-2025 yillarda yoshlarning kitobxonlik madaniyatini jadal rivojlantirish, ularning intellektual salohiyati o'sishi hisobiga inson kapitali sifatini yaxshilash kabi muhim mezonlar belgilangan.

Shuningdek, aholi, avvalo, yoshlarning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy, badiiy-estetik talablariga javob beradigan kitoblarni yuksak sifat bilan chop etish, nashriyotlar va ijodkorlar faoliyatiga ko'maklashish, bolalarga mo'ljallangan adabiyotlarni chop etishni qo'llab-quvvatlash, milliy va jahon adabiyotining eng sara namunalarini tarjima qilish, mutolaa madaniyatini yuksaltirish, respublikaning olis hududlarida va yoshga doir kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish, aholining kitobxonlik darajasi va kitobga qiziqishini tizimli o'rganib borish, kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan loyiha va tanlovlarni tashkil etish kabi dolzarb vazifalar ko'zda tutilgan.

Kitobxonlikni rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan chora-tadbirlar samaradorligini baholash tizimini ishlab chiqish, «Eng yaxshi kitobxon hudud», «Eng yaxshi kitobxon mahalla», «Eng yaxshi kitobxon ta'lim muassasasi» kabi reytinglarni joriy etish va boshqa muhim vazifalar belgilangan.

Kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik ahamiyatini quyidagicha ifodalash mumkin:

1. Intellektual va shaxsiy rivojlanish Kitobxonlik madaniyati shakllantirish orqali o'quvchilar va yoshlar nafaqat bilim olishadi, balki intellektual va shaxsiy rivojlanish uchun zarur bo'lgan asoslarga ega bo'lishadi. Kitoblarni o'qish kishining dunyoqarashini kengaytiradi, o'z fikrini mustaqil ravishda rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga,

ularning aqliy faolligi ortadi, va mustahkam bilim asosida muammolarga yechim topishga qodir bo'ladilar.

2. Axloqiy-estetik tarbiya Kitoblar nafaqat ilmiy bilimlarni, balki axloqiy va estetik qadriyatlarni ham o'rgatadi. Klassik adabiyotlar, felsefi asarlar, badiiy asarlar insonni ma'naviy jihatdan to'ldiradi, uning ahloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantiradi. Kitobxonlik madaniyati axloqiy va estetik tarbiya masalalarida ham ijtimoiy muhim rol o'ynaydi. Kitoblar orqali yoshlar o'zlarining ichki dunyosini anglab, haqiqat va adolat, do'stlik va sadoqat, vatanparvarlik kabi insoniy qadriyatlarni anglash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

3. Pedagogik jarayonda kitoblar va o'qishning roli ta'lim tizimida kitoblarning roli beqiyosdir. Kitoblar nafaqat ta'limning ilmiy poydevorini yaratadi, balki pedagogik jarayonda o'qituvchining hamkoriga aylanadi. Kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda o'qituvchining rolini e'tiborga olish zarur. U kitoblarni o'quvchilarga tanishtirishda, ularga o'qishni qiziqarli va foydali qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bundan tashqari, o'qituvchi o'quvchilarga kitoblarni to'g'ri tanlash va ulardan foydalanish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar berishi lozim.

4. Jamoaviy va madaniy taraqqiyot kitoblar jamoaviy madaniyatni rivojlantirishda ham katta rol o'ynaydi. Ular odamlar o'rtasidagi kommunikatsiyani, tushunishni va axborot almashinuvini osonlashtiradi. Kitobxonlik madaniyati nafaqat individual o'qish jarayoni, balki jamoa bilan birgalikda o'qish, munozaralar o'tkazish, fikrlarni almashish kabi ijtimoiy jarayonlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Bunday faoliyatlar orqali insonlar o'rtasida do'stlik, hurmat va bir-birini tushunish hissi mustahkamlanadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, "Tarbiya" darslarida kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish o'quvchilarning ma'naviy dunyosini boyitish, ularda yuksak axloqiy fazilatlarini tarbiyalashning muhim shartidir. Bu jarayon uzluksiz, tizimli va maqsadli ravishda olib borilishi, unda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikka alohida e'tibor qaratilishi lozim. Zero, bugun kitobga oshno bo'lgan yoshlar ertaga mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo'shadigan barkamol shaxslar bo'lib yetishadilar.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. O'zbekiston prezidentining 2017 yil 13 sentyabrdagi "Kitob mahsulotlarini nashr etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ib qilish bo'yicha kompleks choratadbirlar dasturi to'g'risida"gi qarori
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INKLYUZIV TA'LIMDA MUAMMO VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI

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Annonatsiya: Bu maqola "Inklyuziv Ta'lim: Xalqaro Tajriba va Amaliyot, Erishilgan Natijalar, Muammo va Ularning Yechimlari" mavzusida yozilgan. Maqola inklyuziv ta'limning xalqaro tarixini, uning erishilgan natijalarini va ulardan foydalanishning

muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu mavzu bilan bog'liq xalqaro tajribalar, inklyuziv ta'limning amaliyotlari, muammoatlari va ularning yechimlari tahlil qilinadi. Maqola inklyuziv ta'limning dunyo bo'ylab qanday o'zgarishlarni olib kelishi va undagi muhim huquqiy muammolarni bayon qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Inklyuziv ta'lim, xalqaro tajriba, natija, ta'lim usullari, muammo, yechim.

Inklyuziv ta'limning xalqaro tarixi, 20-asrning boshlariga qaytib boshlanadi, lekin o'sayotgan yillarda uning rivojlanishida katta o'zgarishlar bo'ldi. Bu tizim, avvalo, Engellilarning ta'limiga o'girilgan, ammo keyin, bu tajriba boshqa o'rganuvchilar uchun ham foydalanishga olib kelindi. Xalqaro tajribalar, ko'pgina mamlakatlarda inklyuziv ta'limning qanday amalga oshirilishini tajriba qilishda katta o'rin egalladi. Asosiy tajribalar, inklyuziv ta'limning har bir talabasi uchun o'zlashtirilgan darslar va ta'lim usullari sifatida qanday qo'llanilishini ko'rsatadigan sabablardan biri sifatida ta'riflanadi. Xalqaro daraja, inklyuziv ta'limning boshqa mamlakatlarda ko'rsatilishi va bu sohada o'zgarishlar olib kelishi natijasida yuzaga chiqdi. Bu tizim dunyo bo'ylab o'rganuvchan ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi va o'rganuvchilar uchun o'zlarining potensialini maksimal darajada ishlab chiqarishda yordam beradi. Inklyuziv ta'limning xalqaro tarixi, ta'lim tizimlarining inson huquqlarini bajarish va har bir o'rganuvchi uchun o'zlashtirilgan ta'limni ta'minlash maqsadida qanday rivojlanayotganligini o'rganish uchun katta muhimlikka ega. Inklyuziv ta'limning boshqa turlari bilan solishtirilganda, unda o'rganuvchilar uchun erishilgan natijalar va ulardan foydalanishning xalqaro miqyosdagi o'rnini ta'kidlash juda muhimdir. Erishilgan natijalar, o'rganuvchilarning o'qish va o'rganish jarayonlari natijasida paydo bo'layotgan bilimlar, ko'nikmalar, va tajribalar hisoblanadi. Bu natijalar har bir o'rganuvchi uchun maxsusdir va ularning o'zlashtirilishiga yordam beradi.

Erishilgan natijalar xalqaro darajada ham o'rganuvchilar uchun o'zlashtirilgan bilim va ko'nikmalarni ta'minlaydi. Bu, ularning dunyo bo'ylab o'zgarishlar va boshqa mamlakatlar bilan o'zaro almashishlari uchun asosiy manba bo'lib, ulardan foydalanish ularni dunyo bo'ylab mustaqil hayotlari uchun tayyorlaydi. O'rganuvchilar o'zlarining o'qish va o'rganish natijalarini xalqaro miqyosda qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi, ularni dunyo bo'ylab huquqiy jihatdan o'zlarining bilimlarini o'zlashtirish va bu bilimlarni ishlab chiqarishga olib keladi. Bu, ularning rivojlanishi va mustaqil hayotlari uchun muhimdir. Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida o'rganuvchilar o'zlarining erishilgan natijalarini qo'llash uchun bir nechta usullarni o'rgana olishadi. Bu usullar, ta'limda o'rgatilgan bilim va ko'nikmalarini amaliy hayotda foydalanishga olib keladi. O'rganuvchilar o'zlarining erishilgan natijalarini ta'limdan tashqari hayotlarida qo'llash uchun ma'naviy va amaliy usullarni qo'llaydilar. Bular orasida, o'zlarining so'nggi maqbul bo'lgan bilim va ko'nikmalarni qo'llash, ulardan mustaqil hayotlarida foydalanish, va shaxsiy rivojlanishlariga yordam berish, muhimdir. Inklyuziv ta'limning muammolari, o'rganuvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun o'zlashtirilgan ta'lim tizimlarini amalga oshirishda muhim masalalardir. Bu muammolarni hal qilish, o'rganuvchilarni, har bir insonni o'zlashtirish uchun kerak bo'lgan yechimlarni o'rgatishga yordam beradi.

Quyidagi qisqa ma'lumotlarda, inklyuziv ta'limning muammolari va ularning yechimlari haqida ko'proq ma'lumot olishingiz mumkin:

Muammolari: 1. Har bir o'rganuvchining xususiyliklari: O'rganuvchilar o'zlarining ta'lim stili va o'rganish usullari bo'yicha farqli xususiyatlarga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Bu o'qituvchilarga har bir o'rganuvchi uchun eng muhim va foydali ta'lim usullarini tanlashda yordam berishni talab qiladi.

2. Huquqiy muammolar: O'rganuvchilar o'rtasida yashirin diskriminatsiya, intizomliso'zlar va qo'llash tizimi bilan bog'liq huquqiy muammolar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. O'qituvchilar bu muammolarni aniqlash va ularni yechish uchun huquqiy muammolarni o'rganishi va yechim topishi kerak.

3. Ta'lim vositalari va materiallari: Ta'lim vositalari va materiallari, har bir o'rganuvchi uchun eng qulay va foydali ko'rsatkichlar bilan ta'minlanishi kerak. Bu o'rganuvchilar o'zlarining o'rganish potensialini oshirish va ta'limni samarali qilish uchun muhimdir.

Yechimlari: 1. Ma'naviy sabr va tajribalilik: O'qituvchilar o'rganuvchilarni ko'rib chiqishda sabrli va ma'naviy tajribali bo'lishlari kerak. Har bir o'rganuvchi uchun o'zgaruvchan davom etadigan jarayonlar mavjud bo'lishi mumkin va o'qituvchilar uning tajribalarini tushuntirib chiqarishi kerak.

2. Huquqiy bilimlar va tushunchalar: O'qituvchilar o'rganuvchilarning huquqiy huquq va tushunchalari haqidagi bilimlarga ega bo'lishlari kerak. Bu o'rganuvchilar uchun to'g'ri muammolarni tushuntirish, ularga yordam bera olish va huquqiy himoya ta'minlashda muhimdir.

3. Individualistik ravishda ishlash: O'rganuvchilarni individual ravishda yaxshi ko'rib chiqish va ularga o'zlarining eng yaxshi tajribalarini taqdim etish imkoniyatini oshirish muhimdir. Bu har bir o'rganuvchi uchun eng samarali o'rganish jarayonini ta'minlashda o'qituvchilar uchun yechimdir.

4. Ijodkorlik va yaratuvchilik: O'rganuvchilarni ijodkorlik va yaratuvchilikka tayyorlash, ularga yengil ish yaratish va jamiyatda qatnashishni o'rganish uchun muhimdir. Inklyuziv ta'lim bu qobiliyatni rivojlantirish va ta'lim jarayonida erkinlikni ta'minlash uchun mos manbalar taqdim etadi. Inklyuziv ta'limning muammolari va yechimlari, har bir o'rganuvchi uchun eng yaxshi ta'lim tajribasini ta'minlash va o'rganuvchilarni o'zlarining eng yaxshi potentsiallarini oshirishni maqsad qiladi. O'qituvchilar uchun, har bir o'rganuvchi uchun eng muhim va qo'llaniladigan ta'lim usullarini topish va ulardan foydalanish, inklyuziv ta'limning amalda yutishining muhim qismi bo'ladi.

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AXBOROTLARNI TIZIMLI TAHLIL QILISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy axborot jamiyatida ma'lumotlarni tizimli tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari va amaliy qo'llanilishini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotda axborot tahlilining metodologik yondashuvlari, tizimli tahlilning asosiy tamoyillari va bosqichlari batafsilroq ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqolada axborotlarni saralash, baholash va sintez qilish jarayonlari, shuningdek, zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida axborot tahlilini samarali amalga oshirish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, tizimli

yondashuv axborot sifatini oshirish, qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonini yaxshilash va tashkiliy samaradorlikni ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot tahlili, tizimli yondashuv, ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash, axborot tizimi, qarorlar qabul qilish, metodologiya, axborot texnologiyalari

Abstract: This article examines the theoretical foundations and practical applications of systematic information analysis in the modern information society. The research explores methodological approaches to information analysis, fundamental principles and stages of systematic analysis in detail. The article analyzes the processes of information filtering, evaluation and synthesis, as well as ways to effectively implement information analysis using modern technologies. The research results demonstrate that a systematic approach plays a crucial role in improving information quality, enhancing decision-making processes, and ensuring organizational efficiency.

Keywords: information analysis, systematic approach, data processing, information system, decision making, methodology, information technology

Zamonaviy dunyoda axborot eng qimmatli resurslardan biriga aylangan. Har kuni global miqyosda ulkan hajmdagi ma'lumotlar yaratilmoqda va tarqatilmoqda. Ushbu sharoitda axborotlarni to'g'ri tahlil qilish va undan samarali foydalanish qobiliyati muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish - bu ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, qayta ishlash, baholash va ulardan mantiqiy xulosalar chiqarish jarayonining murakkab va ko'p qirrali uslubidir. Tizimli tahlil tushunchasi XX asrning o'rtalarida paydo bo'lgan bo'lsada, hozirgi kunda u yangi ma'no va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Raqamli texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi, sun'iy intellekt va katta ma'lumotlar sohasidagi yutuqlar axborotlarni tahlil qilishning yangi imkoniyatlarini yaratdi. Shu bilan birga, axborot oqimining ortishi, noto'g'ri va soxta ma'lumotlarning tarqalishi tizimli yondashuvni yanada zarur qilmoqda. Axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish nafaqat individual foydalanuvchilar, balki tashkilotlar, davlat organlari va butun jamiyat uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu jarayon strategik rejalashtirish, raqobatbardosh afzalliklarni aniqlash, xavflarni baholash va samarali qarorlar qabul qilish uchun zarurdir.

Tizimli tahlil - bu murakkab ob'ektlar, jarayonlar yoki vaziyatlarni ularning barcha elementlari, aloqalari va o'zaro ta'siri kontekstida o'rganish metodidir. Ushbu yondashuv asosida tizim nazariyasi, kibernetika, axborot nazariyasi va boshqa ilmiy yo'nalishlarning yutuqlari yotadi. Tizimli tahlilning asosiy tamoyillari quyidagilardan iborat: yaxlitlik tamoyili, ierarxiya tamoyili, tizimning tashqi muhit bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi, maqsadga yo'naltirilganlik va ko'p variantlilik tamoyillari. Yaxlitlik tamoyili tizimni uning alohida elementlari yig'indisidan ko'proq narsa sifatida ko'rib chiqishni anglatadi. Ierarxiya tamoyili esa tizim tarkibiy qismlarining turli darajadagi tuzilishini tan oladi. Axborotlarni tizimli tahlil qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan yana bir konsepsiya - bu axborot qiymatining nisbiy xususiyatidir.

Axborotlarni tahlil qilishda turli metodologik yondashuvlar qo'llaniladi. Ularning asosiylarini quyidagicha tasniflash mumkin: Kontent-tahlil metodi matnli ma'lumotlarni tizimli ravishda o'rganish va miqdoriy hamda sifat jihatidan baholashga qaratilgan. Bu usul axborot oqimlarida muayyan mavzular, tendentsiyalar yoki muammolarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Kontent-tahlil jarayonida matn kategoriyalarga ajratiladi, asosiy tushunchalar va ularning takrorlanish chastotasi aniqlanadi.

Qiyosiy tahlil turli manbalardan olingan axborotlarni qiyoslash va taqqoslash orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bu yondashuv axborotning ishonchligini tekshirish, ziddiyatlarni aniqlash va to'liqroq tasavvur hosil qilish uchun muhimdir. Komparativ tahlilda ma'lumotlarning kelib chiqishi, muallif obro'si va kontekstual omillar hisobga olinadi. Strukturaviy tahlil axborotni

tarkibiy qismlarga ajratish va ular orasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganishga asoslanadi. Bu usul murakkab axborot tizimlarini tushinish va ularning ichki mantiqini ochib berishda samarali hisoblanadi. Strukturaviy tahlil jarayonida axborotning elementlari, ularning funktsiyalari va o'zaro ta'siri aniqlanadi.

Dinamik tahlil axborotning vaqt o'tishi bilan qanday o'zgarishini kuzatish va tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Bu yondashuv tendentsiyalarni aniqlash, prognozlar tuzish va rivojlanish yo'nalishlarini bashorat qilishda qo'llaniladi. Dinamik tahlil tarixiy ma'lumotlar va joriy holatni o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. Tizimli-funksional tahlil axborot tizimlarini ularning funktsiyalari va maqsadlari nuqtai nazaridan ko'rib chiqadi. Bu yondashuv tizimning har bir elementi qanday vazifa bajarishini va umumiy maqsadga qanday hissa qo'shishini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Axborotlarni samarali tahlil qilish uchun aniq tuzilgan jarayonni amalga oshirish zarur. Tizimli tahlilning asosiy bosqichlari quyidagilardan iborat: Birinchi bosqich - muammo yoki vazifani aniqlash. Ushbu bosqichda tahlil maqsadi aniq belgilanadi, asosiy savollar shakllantiriladi va kutilayotgan natijalar belgilab olinadi. Maqsadning aniq bo'lishi keyingi barcha jarayonlarning samaradorligini ta'minlaydi. Shu bosqichda tahlil doirasi, cheklovlar va muvaffaqiyat mezonlari ham aniqlanadi.

Ikkinchi bosqich - axborot manbalarini aniqlash va tanlash. Bu jarayonda mavzu bo'yicha mavjud axborot manbalari ro'yxati tuziladi, ularning ishonchligi va dolzarbligi baholanadi. Manbalar rasmiy hujjatlar, ilmiy nashrlar, statistik ma'lumotlar, ekspert fikrlari, ommaviy axborot vositalari va boshqa manbalar bo'lishi mumkin. Har bir manbaning kuchli va zaif tomonlari hisobga olinadi.

Uchinchi bosqich - axborotlarni yig'ish va tizimlashtirish. Tanlangan manbalardan tegishli ma'lumotlar to'planadi va ma'lum tartibda joylashtiriladi. Bu jarayonda axborotning hajmi, formati va strukturasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Zamonaviy sharoitda bu bosqichda raqamli vositalar va ma'lumotlar bazalari keng qo'llaniladi.

To'rtinchi bosqich - axborotlarning haqiqiylikini tekshirish va baholash. Yig'ilgan ma'lumotlarning aniqligini, ishonchligini va dolzarbligini tekshirish amalga oshiriladi. Bu bosqich soxta yoki noto'g'ri axborotlarni saralash uchun juda muhimdir. Baholash mezonlari orasida manbaning nufuzi, ma'lumotning tasdiqlanish darajasi, mantiqiy izchilligi va boshqa omillar mavjud.

Beshinchi bosqich - axborotlarni tahlil qilish va talqin etish. Tasdiqlangan ma'lumotlar ustida chuqur tahlil ishlari olib boriladi. Bu jarayonda axborotlar o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlar aniqlanadi, naqshlar va tendentsiyalar ochib beriladi, sabab-oqibat munosabatlari o'rganiladi. Tahlil natijasida ma'lumotlar ma'noga ega bilimga aylanadi.

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